

2026 AERA Annual Meeting Complete PDF Program

Tuesday, April 7th, 8:00 am

SIG Sessions

1.010. SIG-93 Research on Learning and Instruction in Physical Education Invisible College. SIG-Research on Learning and Instruction in Physical Education; Pre-Conference Mentoring Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
8:00am to 4:00pm

Chair: *Kelly L. Simonton, University of Wyoming*

1.011. Chinese American Educational Research and Development Association Annual Meeting. Affiliated Groups; Panel Discussion
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Boyle Heights; 8:00am to 5:00pm

1.012. Chinese American Educational Research and Development Association Annual Meeting. Affiliated Groups; Panel Discussion
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Ladera Heights; 8:00am to 5:00pm

1.013. Coalition Advancing Knowledge and Impact. Affiliated Groups; Workshop
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 6th Floor, Metropolitan; 8:00am to 6:00pm

1.014. Society for the Study of Curriculum History Annual Meeting (Day 1). Affiliated Groups; Panel Discussion
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 6th Floor, Broadway; 8:00am to 6:00pm

Tuesday, April 7th, 9:00 am

Professional Development Courses

2.010. PD26-01 Developing Theory Through Qualitative Inquiry. Professional Development and Training Committee; Professional Development Course
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum F;
9:00am to 5:00pm

Director: *Johmy Saldaña, Arizona State University*

2.011. PD26-02 Approaches to Evaluating Educational Programs. Professional Development and Training Committee; Professional Development Course

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum G; 9:00am to 5:00pm

Instructors: *Bianca Montrosse-Moorhead, University of Connecticut; Lyssa Wilson Becho, Western Michigan University; Daniela Schroeter, Western Michigan University*

2.012. PD26-03 Generative AI Literacy for Educational Researchers: Understanding Systems, Applications, and Implications. Professional Development and Training Committee; Professional Development Course
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Platinum H & I;
9:00am to 5:00pm

Directors: *Peter W. Foltz, University of Colorado - Boulder; Golnaz Arastoopour Irgens, Vanderbilt University*

2.013. PD26-04 Introduction to Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. Professional Development and Training Committee; Professional Development Course
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Plaza III;
9:00am to 5:00pm

Instructors: *Amy L. Dent, University of California - Irvine; Terri D. Pigott, Georgia State University; Joshua R. Polanin, American Institutes for Research; Joseph Taylor, University of Colorado - Colorado Springs/AIR*

2.014. PD26-05 Multilevel Modeling with International Large-Scale Assessment Databases Using R. Professional Development and Training Committee; Professional Development Course
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Plaza II;
9:00am to 5:00pm

Director: *Francis H. Lim Huang, University of Missouri*
Instructors: *Umut Atasever, IEA Hamburg; Andrés Christiansen, Katholieke Universiteit Leuven; Alec Kennedy, IEA Hamburg*

2.015. PD26-06 Quantitative Tools for Qualitative Data Analysis: A Truly Equal Status Data Science Design for Transparency, Rigorosity, and Data Science StoryTelling. Professional Development and Training Committee; Professional Development Course
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Plaza I;
9:00am to 5:00pm

Division Sessions

2.016. Division A Executive Committee (Closed Meeting). Division A - Administration; Reception
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, K-Town; 9:00am to 12:00pm

Chair: *Detra DeVerne Johnson, University of Houston*

2.017. Division A VP and Executive Committee Workshop and Strategic Planning Session. Division A - Administration; Pre-Conference Mentoring Session
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 6th Floor, Royal;
9:00am to 12:00pm

Chair: *Detra DeVerne Johnson, University of Houston*

SIG Sessions

2.018. Arts-Based Educational Research SIG Pre Conference Mentoring Session. SIG-Arts-Based Educational Research; Pre-Conference Mentoring Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond
10; 9:00am to 4:00pm

Chair: *Rhianna K. Thomas, New Mexico State University*

2.019. Arts-Based Educational Research SIG Pre Conference Mentoring Session (Room Five). SIG-Arts-Based Educational Research; Pre-Conference Mentoring Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 6;
9:00am to 4:00pm

Chair: *Rhianna K. Thomas, New Mexico State University*

2.020. Arts-Based Educational Research SIG Pre Conference Mentoring Session (Room Four). SIG-Arts-Based Educational Research; Pre-Conference Mentoring Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 7;
9:00am to 4:00pm

Chair: *Rhianna K. Thomas, New Mexico State University*

2.021. Arts-Based Educational Research SIG Pre Conference Mentoring Session (Room Three). SIG-Arts-Based Educational Research; Pre-Conference Mentoring Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 8;
9:00am to 4:00pm

Chair: *Rhianna K. Thomas, New Mexico State University*

2.022. Arts-Based Educational Research SIG Pre Conference Mentoring Session (Room Two). SIG-Arts-Based Educational Research; Pre-Conference Mentoring Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 9;
9:00am to 4:00pm

Chair: *Rhianna K. Thomas, New Mexico State University*

2.023. Pre-Conference Session: Council of Professors of Instructional Supervision. SIG-Supervision and Instructional Leadership; Pre-Conference Mentoring Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 501A;
9:00am to 5:00pm

Tuesday, April 7th, 10:00 am

Division Sessions

3.010. Division K Tour - A Storied Past: Tracing Education and Activism in LA. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education Cosponsored with Spotlight on Los Angeles and the Region; Off-Site Visit

Division K Historical Tour of Los Angeles, Division K
Historical Tour of Los Angeles; 10:00am to 5:00pm

Chairs: *Nicol R. Howard, Chapman University; Erica D. McCray, University of Florida; Kimberly A. White-Smith, University of San Diego*

Participants: *Niki Elliott, University of San Diego; Annamarie M. Francois, University of California - Los Angeles*

SIG Sessions

3.011. Critical Posthuman and Postfoundational Studies SIG Pre-Conference Mentoring Session. SIG-Critical Posthuman and Postfoundational Studies in Education; Pre-Conference Mentoring Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum
A; 10:00am to 3:00pm

Chair: *Kathryn J. Strom, California State University - East Bay*

Tuesday, April 7th, 11:30 am

SIG Sessions

4.010. AERA Second Language Research SIG Pre-Conference Mentoring Session. SIG-Second Language Research; Pre-Conference Mentoring Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304B;
11:30am to 2:00pm

Chairs: *Kongji Qin, New York University; Christine Montecillo Leider, University of Massachusetts - Lowell*

Participants: *Caitlin G. Fine, Metropolitan State University of Denver; Matt DeRoo, Florida International University; Shuzhan Li, Ithaca College*

Tuesday, April 7th, 12:00 pm

AERA Related Activities

5.010. AERA Institute on Studying Educational Access and

Opportunities (Invitation Only). AERA Related Activities; Pre-Conference Mentoring Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum C; 12:00-7:30pm

Chair: *George L. Wimberly, American Educational Research Association*

Division Sessions

5.011. Division G Pre-Conference Session: Reimagining Research in Context: Dialogues on History, Society, and Futurity in Education. Division G - Social Context of Education; Pre-Conference Mentoring Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 309;
12:00-4:00pm

Chairs: *Cleveland Hayes, Indiana University - Indianapolis; Lasana D. Kazembe, Indiana University - Indianapolis; Erica R. Davila, Lewis University*

SIG Sessions

5.012. Pre-Conference Mentoring Session with the Cultural-Historical Research SIG. SIG-Cultural-Historical Research; Pre-Conference Mentoring Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304C;
12:00-3:00pm

Officers: *Shirin Vossoughi, Northwestern University; Peter Hick, Edge Hill University; Sharon Chang, Teachers College, Columbia University; Na Lor, Teachers College, Columbia University; Yehyang Lee, Syracuse University; Karlyn R. Adams-Wiggins, Portland State University*

Tuesday, April 7th, 1:00 pm

Division Sessions

6.010. Division H Early Career/Graduate Student In-Progress Research Roundtable. Division H - Research, Evaluation and Assessment in Schools; Pre-Conference Mentoring Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
1:00-5:00pm

Chairs: *Hanhui Bao, University of Tennessee; Omayya Horton, University of Massachusetts - Amherst*

6.011. Division K Pre-Conference Seminar Food Room.

Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Reception
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304A;
1:00-9:00pm

Participants: *Nicol R. Howard, Chapman University; Erica D. McCray, University of Florida; Kimberly A. White-Smith, University of San Diego*

6.012. Early Career Pre-Conference Seminar - "Unforgetting Histories and Imagining Futures" as Transformative Praxis for Equity- and Justice-Oriented Early-Career Scholar Development. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Pre-Conference Mentoring Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 301A;
1:00-7:00pm

Chairs: *Taryrn T.C. Brown, University of Florida; Mariah D. Harmon, Pennsylvania State University; David I. Hernandez-Saca, University of Northern Iowa*

Participants: *Nicol R. Howard, Chapman University; Erica D. McCray, University of Florida; Kimberly A. White-Smith, University of San Diego*

6.013. Graduate Student Pre-Conference Seminar - "Unforgetting Histories and Imagining Futures": Developing Teacher Education Researchers as Transformative Change Agents. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Pre-Conference Mentoring Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 301B;
1:00-7:00pm

Chairs: *Taryrn T.C. Brown, University of Florida; Mariah D. Harmon, Pennsylvania State University; David I. Hernandez-Saca, University of Northern Iowa*

Participants: *Nicol R. Howard, Chapman University; Erica D. McCray, University of Florida; Kimberly A. White-Smith, University of San Diego*

6.014. Scholar Organizer Pre-Conference Seminar - Scholar-Organizers: Confronting Attacks on Our Educational Institutions. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Pre-Conference Mentoring Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 303B;
1:00-7:00pm

Chairs: *Carolina Valdez, California State University - Fullerton; Christina Lincoln-Moore, Alabama A&M University*

Participants: *Nicol R. Howard, Chapman University; Erica D. McCray, University of Florida; Kimberly A. White-Smith, University of San Diego*

SIG Sessions

6.015. Queer Studies SIG Graduate Student Pre-Conference Mentoring Session. SIG-Queer Studies; Pre-Conference Mentoring Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 504;
1:00-5:00pm

Chair: *Roberto C. Orozco, University of Minnesota*

Officers: *Angel D. Gonzalez, California State University - Fresno;*
Jarrel T. Johnson, University of Utah

Tuesday, April 7th, 2:00 pm

SIG Sessions

7.010. CESJ Graduate Student Pre-Conference Forum— "Remembering and Rehearsing Collective Care." SIG-Critical Educators for Social Justice; Pre-Conference Mentoring Session
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Echo Park; 2:00-5:00pm
Chairs: *Re'Nyqua Farrington, University of California - Riverside;*
Justine Dacia Parnell, Arizona State University
Participants: *Kenjus T. Watson, American University; Tiffani Marie, San Jose State University*

Tuesday, April 7th, 2:30 pm

Division Sessions

8.010. Division F Pre-Conference Mentoring Session. Division F - Historical Inquiry in Education; Pre-Conference Mentoring Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 402A; 2:30-7:00pm
Chair: *Jon Hale, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Tuesday, April 7th, 3:00 pm

SIG Sessions

9.010. Special and Inclusive Education Research SIG Pre-Conference Mentoring Session. SIG-Special and Inclusive Education Research; Pre-Conference Mentoring Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304C; 3:00-5:00pm
Officers: *Chelsea Tracy-Bronson, Stockton University; Jessica Ann McQueston, Sam Houston State University; Nickie Coomer, Colorado College*

Tuesday, April 7th, 4:00 pm

Division Sessions

10.010. A Storied Past: Tracing Education and Activism in LA - Post Tour Session. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education Cosponsored with Spotlight on Los Angeles and the Region; Invited Speaker Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 404AB; 4:00-5:00pm

Chairs: *Nicol R. Howard, Chapman University; Erica D. McCray, University of Florida; Kimberly A. White-Smith, University of San Diego*

Participants: *Niki Elliott, University of San Diego; Annamarie M. Francois, University of California - Los Angeles*

10.011. Urban Education Editorial Board Meeting. Affiliated Groups; Board Meeting
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum B; 4:00-7:00pm

Tuesday, April 7th, 4:45 pm

Division Sessions

11.010. K-12 Teacher Pre-Conference Seminar - Retooling AI Learning for Justice: A conversation with educators on the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in schools. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Pre-Conference Mentoring Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 303A; 4:45-7:00pm

Chairs: *Charlotte Achieng-Evensen, Chapman University; Wes Kriesel, Orange County Department of Education*

Participants: *Nicol R. Howard, Chapman University; Erica D. McCray, University of Florida; Kimberly A. White-Smith, University of San Diego*

Tuesday, April 7th, 5:30 pm

SIG Sessions

12.010. CANCELED - William L. Boyd National Educational Politics Workshop. SIG-Politics of Education; Pre-Conference Mentoring Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 408A; 5:30-6:30pm

Wednesday, April 8th, 7:00 am

Committee Sessions

- 13.010. AERA Graduate Student Resource Center (Day 1).** Graduate Student Council; Networking Center
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 502B;
7:00am to 10:00pm
- 13.011. 22nd Roundtable of the International Network on School, Family, and Community Partnerships.** Affiliated Groups; Workshop
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Santa Barbara A; 7:00am to 1:30pm
- 13.012. 22nd Roundtable of the International Network on School, Family, and Community Partnerships.** Affiliated Groups; Workshop
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, San Gabriel C; 7:00am to 1:30pm
- 13.013. 22nd Roundtable of the International Network on School, Family, and Community Partnerships.** Affiliated Groups; Workshop
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Santa Barbara B; 7:00am to 1:30pm

Wednesday, April 8th, 7:10 am

AERA Sessions

- 14.010. AERA Welcoming Orientation for New Members and First-Time Attendees.** AERA Sessions; Invited Speaker Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
7:10-8:40am
Chairs: *Tabbye M. Chavous, American Educational Research Association; Maisha T. Winn, Stanford University; Jerome E. Morris, University of Missouri - St. Louis*

Wednesday, April 8th, 7:45 am

Division Sessions

- 15.010. Division A - Section 1: Leadership Virtual Poster Session.** Division A - Administration; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm
Participants:

- School Leadership Effect on Student Achievement Through Teacher Trust: A Meta-Structural Equation Modeling Approach. *Jingping Sun, University of Alabama; Junqi Lin, University of Alabama*
- Who's Minding the Teachers? Principal Practices That Support Teacher Well-Being in High-Poverty Schools. *Diana Sierra, Florida Atlantic University; Patricia Maslin-Ostrowski, Florida Atlantic University*
- Lessons Learned from the Pandemic to Inform Decision-Making About AI in K-12 Schools. *Andrea Catt, University of Rochester; David E. Miller, University of Rochester; Raffaella Borasi, University of Rochester; Zenon Borys, University of Rochester*
- A Phenomenological Study of Black Female School Administrators and their Stories of Leadership. *Tommy Wells, Bellarmine University; Vanessa Gee, Indiana University - Purdue University at Indianapolis*
- The Emotional Weight of Leadership: Understanding Principals' Worry. *Peleg Dor-Haim, Tel Aviv University*
- Sustainable Spirit: A Case Study of Whole Child Reform Cultivating Wisdom, Courage, Compassion. *Diane Martindale, DePaul University*
- Institutional Digital Leadership and ICT Competency: The Moderating Role of Teaching Experience in Chinese Universities. *Jing Cai, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia; Aida Hanim A Hamid, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia; Mohamed Yusoff Mohd Nor, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia*
- PLCs and Teacher Satisfaction: Mediating Teacher Leadership Across School Types. *wang xueting, East China Normal University; Chen Xie, East China Normal University*
- Getting into the Zone: School principals' work-related flow and its drivers and outcomes. *Junjun Chen, Education University of Hong Kong; Zan Li, The Education University of Hong Kong; Cheng Jin, The Education University of Hong Kong*

- 15.010. Division A - Section 4: School Contexts and Communities Virtual Poster Session.** Division A - Administration; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:
Case Study of Family Engagement in Mathematics Education at a Local Middle School. *Esperanza Ochoa, San Diego State University*

- 15.010. Division B - Section 1: Cultural Inquiry in Curriculum Studies Virtual Poster Session.** Division B - Curriculum Studies; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:
Curricular Erasure And Queer Invisibility: A Content Analysis Of Indian School Textbooks. *Nishtha Saxena, University of*

Delhi; Anya Aggarwal, University of Delhi

15.010. Division B - Section 2: Exploring Past, Present, and Future Curricular Questions Virtual Poster Session.

Division B - Curriculum Studies; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Still Waiting for Superman: A Curricular Retrospective of the No Child Left Behind Era. *Katherine A. Perrotta, Mercer University*

Cultural Memory, Race, and the Secondary English Canon. *Dorothea M. Anagnostopoulos, University of Connecticut; Austin Jerrod Unowitz, University of Connecticut*

Exploring and Teaching LGBTQ+ Labor Histories. *Adam I. Attwood, Austin Peay State University; Niklaus Ryker K. Christensen, Austin Peay State University*

15.010. Division B - Section 3: Theories, Methodologies, and Philosophies of Curriculum Studies Virtual Poster Session.

Division B - Curriculum Studies; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Entanglement with the Hidden Curriculum of Grading. *Kirsten Robbins, SUNY - College at Oneonta; Ann Fradkin-Hayslip, SUNY - College at Oneonta*

15.010. Division B - Section 6: De/Colonization and Transformative Curriculum Studies Virtual Poster Session.

Division B - Curriculum Studies; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

“And a take-apart seal in a pear tree...”: MACOS and Material Histories of Playful Pedagogies. *Nicole K. Weinberg, Texas Christian University*

15.010. Division C - Section 1a: Literacy Virtual Poster Session.

Division C - Learning and Instruction; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Parent and Student Perspectives on Writing and Literacy: Listening to Diverse Voices. *Roselyn Gishen*

Maternal Literacy Practices and Vocabulary Development in Preschool Children. *Anosha Islam, Air University; Lauren R. Franklin, Baby Talk Child Development Lab; Fizza Farrukh, Air University*

15.010. Division C - Section 1c: Mathematics Virtual Poster Session.

Division C - Learning and Instruction; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Unraveling the Psychological and Behavioral Dynamics of Classroom Improvement: Insights from TALIS Shanghai Data. *Weitong Liu, Shandong University; Yuxuan Yan, Shandong University; Xinwei Chang, University of Glasgow; Hui Zhang, Shandong University*

15.010. Division C - Section 1e: Engineering and Computer Science Virtual Poster Session.

Division C - Learning and Instruction; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Programming Learning Supported by Generative Artificial Intelligence: Student Programming Performance and Cognitive Load. *Heng Zhang, University of Hong Kong; Jing Zhang, Universiti Sains Malaysia*

Understanding Data Story Construction with a Narrative Comprehension Lens: Implications for Learning Design. *Jennifer Posada, University of Maryland - Baltimore County; Yetunde Okueso, University of Maryland - Baltimore County; Louise G. Yarnall, SRI International; Hui Yang, SRI International; Lujie Karen Chen, University of Maryland - Baltimore County*

Improving the Spatial Visualization Skills of College Engineering Students by Using an Explicit Instruction Approach. *Yi Ding, Fordham University; Qian Wang, New York University; Jiayi Wang, University of Houston; Qiong Yu, Queens College - CUNY*

15.010. Division C - Section 2a: Cognitive and Motivational Processes Virtual Poster Session.

Division C - Learning and Instruction; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Nature, Predictors, and Outcomes of Students' Motivation Profiles: A Longitudinal Person-Centered Approach. *Mouhamadou Thiam, Université de Moncton; Nicole Lirette-Pitre, University of Moncton*

The Relationship of Sources of Research Self-Efficacy Profiles with Research Outcome Expectancy and Self-Efficacy. *Leigh M. Harrell-Williams, University of Memphis; Eli Andrew Jones, University of Memphis; Luke Walden, Union University*

Linking Growth Mindset and Academic Coping to Grit and Self-Handicapping Behaviors in Neurodiverse Adolescents (Poster 10). *Rahma F. Goran, Temple University; Cabi Wang, Temple University; Jay Tarnoff, Immaculata*

University; Xu Jiang, Temple University

15.010. Division C - Section 2b: Learning and Motivation in Social and Cultural Contexts Virtual Poster Session.

Division C - Learning and Instruction; Virtual iPresentation Only

Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Is Translanguaging Universal? A Systematic Review Across Global Language Contexts. *Yueqing Zhong, George Mason University*

Growth Mindset, Stress, & Test Anxiety in Middle School Students. *Eva M Lucignano, Rowan University; Tenelle Porter, Rowan University*

Post-COVID-19 Era: Improving Learning and Reducing Violence through Successful Educational Actions at a Brazilian School. *Roseli Rodrigue de Mello, University of Sao Carlos; Antonio Alvaro Soares Zuin, Universidade Federal de São Carlos; Bruno Cortegoso Prezenszky, Universidade Federal de São Carlos; Denise Bachega, University of San Carlos*

Bridging Theory and Practice: How AI Feedback Can Enhance Learning Assistants' Pedagogical Flexibility in STEM Classrooms. *Ramadhan Mubarak Hamisi, University of Colorado - Boulder*

15.010. Division C - Section 3a: Learning Environments Virtual Poster Session.

Division C - Learning and Instruction; Virtual iPresentation Only

Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Practitioner Perspectives on Public Speaking Education in K-12 Schools: An Implementation Science Approach. *Lauren Biegley, Lehigh University; Brook Sawyer, Lehigh University*

15.010. Division D - Section 1: Measurement, Psychometrics, and Assessment Virtual Poster Session.

Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Virtual iPresentation Only

Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Differential Item Functioning of Personal and Social Responsibility Questionnaire among School and University Students: An Application of Propensity Score-Based Multidimensional Item Response Theory. *Amal Alhadabi, Sultan Qaboos University*

A Large Language Model-Based Framework for Automated and Accurate Chinese Essay Evaluation. *Yana Xia, East China Normal University; Xiang Feng, East China Normal University*

Robust Estimation of 2PL IRT Parameters via Deep Learning under Non-Ideal Testing Conditions. *Yunbo Yang, University of Chicago*

Development of a Multidimensional Cognitive Ability CAT Using Neural Network Graded Modeling. *Wen Sun, Beijing University of Chinese Medicine; Zichen Liu, Beijing University of Chinese Medicine; Wenjie Xu, Beijing University of Chinese Medicine; Lei Quan, Beijing University of Chinese Medicine; Zongshuo Sha, Beijing University of Chinese Medicine; Yixing Liu, Beijing University of Chinese Medicine*

Deepening Understanding of Common Persons Design in Score Equating: A Simulation Study. *Jiayi Liu, Peking University; Zhehan Jiang, Peking University; Tianpeng Zheng, Peking University; Shicong Feng, Peking University*

Developing a Measure of Spiritual, Emotional, and Physical Dimensions of College Student Well-being. *Kim Proctor, California State University - Dominguez Hills*

Beyond the Noise: Uncovering the Effects of Careless Respondents in Cognitive Diagnostic Modeling. *Tugay Kaçak, Trakya University; Mehtap Aktaş, Trakya University*

From Past Debates to Future Visions: Modelling Generic Problem-Solving Competence in PISA 2012. *Lan Anh Nguyen Khoa, University of Melbourne; Mark R. Wilson, University of California - Berkeley; Cuc Thi Kim Nguyen, University of Melbourne; Matthew Gordon Ray Courtney, Nazarbayev University*

Validating an Instrument for Students' Personal Learning Device Acceptance, Use and Self-Directed Home-Based Learning. *Hwee Lee Seah, MOE; Choon Lang Quek, National Institute of Education, Nanyang Technological University*

15.010. Division D - Section 2: Statistical Theory and Quantitative Methods Virtual Poster Session.

Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Virtual iPresentation Only

Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Understanding Burnout Among Korean Elementary School Teachers: A Post-Selection Inference Analysis. *SUNGMIN LEE, Korea National University of Education; Jin Eun Yoo, Korea National University of Education*

Evolving Themes in Educational Research: A Structural Topic Modeling of AERA Journals. *Nurcan Kahraman, Bursa Uludag University; Rumeysa Beyazhancer, Bursa Uludag University*

15.010. Division D - Section 3: Qualitative Methodologies Virtual Poster Session.

Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Virtual iPresentation Only

Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Extending Narrative Inquiry and Autoethnography in Relation to Dewey's Theory of Experience. *Yi (Jenny) Li, University of Ottawa*

Analyzing Data with AI in an Interview-Based Qualitative Study on Multimodality for Polylingual Higher-Education Students. *Olga Gould-Yakovleva, Independent Researcher*

Bringing Qualitative Studies Together: Aims and Impacts of Meta-Synthesis. *Maria Ong, TERC; Nuria Jaumot-Pascual, TERC; Lisette Esmeralda Torres-Gerald, TERC; Christina Silva, TERC*

Evaluating Transformative Effects of Culture and Arts Education Through Traces of "expériences marquantes." *Lihan YU, École normale supérieure de Lyon (ENS Lyon); Jean-Charles Chabanne, École normale supérieure de Lyon (ENS Lyon)*

15.010. Division D - Section 4: Multiple and Mixed Methodologies Virtual Poster Session. Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Virtual iPresentation Only

Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Mapping the Links Between Maternal Overprotection and Preschoolers' Eating Behaviors: A Mixed Methods Network Study. *Ziqin Liu, Macquarie University*

Exploring Black Student Representation in Dual Enrollment: A Critical Race Mixed Methods Study. *Janelle R Clay, Achieve Atlanta*

15.010. Division G - Section 1: Education and Place, Space, Time Virtual Poster Session. Division G - Social Context of Education; Virtual iPresentation Only

Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

The Great India Coaching Train: Impact of Demand for 'Shadow Higher Education System' on Internal Youth Migration in India. *Tanya Ahuja, Indian Institute of Management*

Resolved to thrive: Cultivating critical consciousness through dialogue, agency, and co-constructed community. *Soe Young Lee, Boston University; Xinyu Gu, Boston University; Jessica Wu, Boston University; Thai Daniel, Boston University; Michael Alan Medina, Boston University*

STEM Undergraduate Students and Short-term Study Abroad Program: An Exploratory Study on Intercultural Competence. *Margaret Gatongi, Virginia Commonwealth University; John Fife, Virginia Commonwealth University*

Cultural superiority, Disdain for mainstream norms among Korean immigrant mothers. *Jung - Ah Choi, St. Peter's University*

Not all Movers are the Same: Residential Mobility and School

Outcomes in a Large Urban School District. *Chenyang Zhou, Western University; Gus Riveros, Western University*

15.010. Division G - Section 2: Differences and Intersectionalities Virtual Poster Session. Division G - Social Context of Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Exploring the Role of African American English and American Sign Language in Shaping Literacy Development. *Alexis Lawton, Clemson University*

Unforgetting Belonging: Rethinking Identity, Language, and Adolescent Loneliness in Global Middle Schools. *Lori Nolte, Wilkes University; Jin Joy Mao, Wilkes University*

Black Women Educators' Experiences With Racial and Gendered Microaggressions in K-12. *Valentina Arango-Correa, Rutgers University - New Brunswick*

15.010. Division G - Section 3: Languages, Literacies, and Representations Virtual Poster Session. Division G - Social Context of Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Belonging and Culturally Sustaining Practices in a School Food Program. *Katie Brubacher, University of Alberta; Sarah Harper, University of Alberta*

15.010. Division G - Section 5: Inquiry, Transformation, and Communities Virtual Poster Session. Division G - Social Context of Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Exploring Generative AI in Education: Large Language Models for Topic Modeling and Discourse Analysis. *Wanli Xing, University of Florida; Fan Zhang, University of Florida*

Hiding higher education equity work in plain sight through a practical application of queer theory. *Kristyn Meyer Wood, Harper College*

Practicing Good Relation: Youth, Grief, and the Ethics of Participatory Research. *Tiffany T. Hill, University of Toronto*

15.010. Division G - Section 6: Inquiry in the Social Context of Education Virtual Poster Session. Division G - Social Context of Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Working the Ruins of "Tiger Mom" Parenting: Educational Strategies of Korean Immigrant Mothers. *Jung - Ah Choi, St. Peter's University*

Determinants of Dual Attainment in Academic Achievement and Wellbeing: Evidence from Korea, U.K., and Finland. *Seulki Kim, Korean Educational Development Institute*

Influencer Culture and Chinese University Students' Perceptions of Higher Education. *Jiwen Yang, University of Macau*

(Re)Imagining National Identity: Chinese Students' Everyday Negotiations in a Transnational Context. *Chufan Qiu, Huazhong University of Science and Technology*

15.010. Division H - Section 1: Applied Research in Schools Virtual Poster Session. Division H - Research, Evaluation and Assessment in Schools; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Youth Inquiry of Traditional Chinese Medicine and Western Medicine Preferences in Local High Schools. *Jianqi Wang, The High School Affiliated to Renmin University of China; Zili Zhang, Pennsylvania State University; Vivian L. Gadsden, University of Pennsylvania*

Who Thrives in the Digital Age? Examining SES, Self-Efficacy, Screen Time, and Digital Literacy. *Hyejeong Lee, University of Texas - San Antonio; Suyoun Kim, Korea University; Tiffany Emanuel, University of Texas - San Antonio*

15.010. Division H - Section 2: Program Evaluation in Schools Virtual Poster Session. Division H - Research, Evaluation and Assessment in Schools; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Virtual or In-Person? Comparative Evaluation of a Pre-health Summer Program for High School Students. *Aihua Wang, Florida State University*

Reimagining ELA for Equity: Evaluating Educative Materials for English Learners Across States. *Zahava Nickell, Empirical Education Inc.; Adam Schellinger, Empirical Education Inc.; Andrew P. Jaciw, Empirical Education Inc.; Aida Walqui, WestEd; Jenna L. Zacamy, Empirical Education Inc.*

15.010. Division H - Section 3: Assessment in Schools Virtual Poster Session. Division H - Research, Evaluation and Assessment in Schools; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Paper-Pencil and Computer Adaptive Test Formats: Comparing Student Psychometrics on a Mathematical Problem-Solving Assessment. *Toni A. May, Binghamton University - SUNY; Gregory E. Stone, University of Toledo; Jonathan D. Bostic, Bowling Green State University; Gabriel Matney, Bowling*

Green State University; Connor J. Sondergeld, MetriKs; Timothy D. Folger, Binghamton University - SUNY; Yiyun Fan, Binghamton University - SUNY

Let Me Help You: Near-Peer Teaching in Multimodal Assessments. *Michelle Raquel, The University of Hong Kong; Wim Isidoor Lea Vergult, The University of Hong Kong; Yan LI, The Education University of Hong Kong*

15.010. Division H - Section 4: Accountability in Schools Virtual Poster Session. Division H - Research, Evaluation and Assessment in Schools; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

From Metrics to Materials: Generative Mechanisms of Formalism in Chinese Educational Inspection. *Hui Zhi, Beijing Normal University*

15.010. Division I - Education in the Professions Virtual Poster Session. Division I - Education in the Professions; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Exploring Roadblocks to Success: Minoritized Medical Students' Experiences of Educational Technologies. *Racheal Lee, Uniformed Services University of the Health Sciences; Steven J. Durning, Uniformed Services University of the Health Sciences; Marina Shapiro, Uniformed Services University of the Health Sciences; Anita Samuel, Uniformed Services University of the Health Sciences*

The Development of an Instrument to Measure Engineering Identity. *Yifan Wang, Fordham University; Yi Ding, Fordham University; Qian Wang, Manhattan College; Alesia Mickle Moldavan, Georgia Southern University*

Undergraduate Engineering Students' Motivation, Self-Efficacy, and Student Adjustment in Relation to Engineering Identity and Academic Achievement. *Yifan Wang, Fordham University; Yi Ding, Fordham University; Qian Wang, Manhattan College; Alesia Mickle Moldavan, Georgia Southern University*

Reliability of Article-Based Testing: Insights from the Omega Coefficient Family. *Qiao Lin, American Board of Psychiatry & Neurology; David Shin, American Board of Psychiatry and Neurology, Inc.; Jeffrey M. Lyness, American Board of Psychiatry and Neurology, Inc.; Huaping Sun, The American Board of Anesthesiology*

15.010. Division J - Section 2a: College Student Access, Trajectories, and Transitions Virtual Poster Session. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

First, Do No Harm. But Can We Do Better? An Evaluation of a Corequisite Reform. *Zeyu Xu, American Institutes for Research; Ben Backes, American Institutes for Research*

Postsecondary Access and Completion: A Meta-Analysis of Dual Enrollment and Early College High School Participation. *Justin C. Ortagus, University of Florida; Xiaodan Hu, Southern Methodist University; Hope Allchin, University of Florida; Rachel Dean Divaker, University of Florida; Terri D. Pigott, Georgia State University*

Building Stackable Education and Career Credentials into Healthcare with Low-Income Students. *Catherine R. Cooper, University of California - Santa Cruz; Lucia Vitale, University of California - Santa Cruz; Jordan Sitea, University of California - Santa Cruz; Cristine H. Chopra, Santa Cruz County Office of Education; Maria Rocha-Ruiz, University of California - Santa Cruz*

15.010. Division J - Section 2c: Assessing College Student Success and Impact Virtual Poster Session. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Predictors of College Degree Completion among Students with Foster Care Experience in California. *Nathanael J. Okpych, University of Connecticut; Jennifer Geiger, University of Illinois at Chicago*

Integrating Canvas Engagement Data and Student Evaluations of Teaching to Predict Academic Performance. *Qingmin Shi, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Shiloh Fling, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Tina Nelson, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*

15.010. Division J - Section 3: Organization, Management, and Leadership Virtual Poster Session. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Crossing the Chasm: Interpretation as the Bridge Between Assessment and Action in Organizational Learning Processes. *Emily Braught, Indiana University*

A Framework for University Contributions to Climate Change: Pathways, Priorities, and Action Models. *Yujie LI, Shanghai Jiao Tong University*

Triangulating Excellence: The Dynamic Interplay Between Regulators, Teaching Centers, and National Forums in Higher Education. *Nizar Bitar, The Max Stern Yezreel Valley College; Nitza Davidovich, Ariel University*

15.010. Division J - Section 4: Faculty, Curriculum, and Teaching Virtual Poster Session. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Virtual iPresentation Only

Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Integrating AI in Higher Education: Faculty Insights on Syllabus Policies and Student Use. *Mahmoud Altalouli, State University of New York Brockport; Amy L. Shema, College at Brockport - SUNY; Jialin Yan, University of Rochester*

Retaining Faculty in Higher Education: Examining the Crucial Role of Sense of Belonging. *Jennifer Reid, Virginia Commonwealth University; Maike I. Philipsen, Virginia Commonwealth University; Julie Charbonnier, Virginia Commonwealth University; Pat Githens, Virginia Commonwealth University; Adelaide Alexander, Virginia Commonwealth University; Mary A. Hermann, Loyola University - New Orleans; Susan Kornstein, Virginia Commonwealth University*

Beyond the Loop: Broadening How We Think About Assessment Use. *Emily Braught, Indiana University*

Classroom Assessment Validity in Dynamic Postsecondary Systems. *Maxine Britto, Brock University; Tiffany L. Gallagher, Brock University*

Toward Transformative UDL Practice: A Community-Based Assessment of Institutional Understanding, Usage, and Cultural Barriers. *Molly McKeon, University of Colorado - Denver*

Learning Together: Student Voices and Experiences in Co-Created Educational Design. *Nataliya Pakhotina, Texas A&M University; Rayyan Zulfiqar, Texas A&M University; Mahjabin Chowdhury, Texas A&M University*

Rethinking the Supplemental Instruction Model to Meet the Needs of Community College Students. *Catherine Mas, n/a; Stephanie J. Jones, Texas Tech University*

Investigating Classroom Patterns and Behaviors Based on Classroom Observation Protocol for Undergraduate STEM (COPUS). *Yousif Muten, Auburn University*

15.010. Division J - Section 6: Society, Culture, History, and Change Virtual Poster Session. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Perpetuating the Devaluation of Historically Feminized Academic Fields: Use of Public Funds in a Formula Funding Approach. *Valerie Paton, Texas Tech University; Catherine Shepard, Texas Tech University; Stephanie J. Jones, Texas Tech University*

Fat-Bodied Learners And College Websites: Will I fit in? *Sara Lucas, Northern Illinois University*

A Study of Chinese College Students' Identification with Traditional Chinese Culture Research Objective. *Hong Zhang, Qufu Normal University; Hanyu Xing, Qufu Normal University, China*

Advancing Reconciliation in Higher Education: Insights from

Student Affairs Professionals. *Danielle Gardiner Milln, University of Alberta*

15.010. Division K - Section 01: Teaching and Teacher Education in the Content Areas Virtual Poster Session.

Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Beyond Teaching: How English Teachers Shape Aspirations. *Yi Feng, Durham University*

Constructing Futures: How Emerging Educators See Math and Literacy Working Together. *Catherine Susin, Brock University; Tiffany L. Gallagher, Brock University*

15.010. Division K - Section 02: Teacher Agency, Activism, and Leadership Virtual Poster Session.

Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

How do Social Networks of STEM Teachers Change after Participating in a Conference? Are These Changes Sustainable Months After? *Adem Ekmekci, Rice University; Bryan Rebar, University of Oregon; Stephanie Salomone, University of Portland; Jenna Porter, California State University - Sacramento; Donna L. Ross, San Diego State University; Jenefer E. Husman, University of Oregon*

Teaching from the Land: Indigenous Educators and the Transformation of Teacher Leadership. *John Kambutu, University of Wyoming; Lydia Nganga, University of Wyoming*

From Streets to Classrooms: Forging and Enacting Teacher Agency in South Korea. *Hyeokeun Kwon, Yonsei University; Won Pyo Hong, Yonsei University; Eunjin Jeong, Yonsei University*

The Commitment to Ethical Teaching Leadership in the Selection of Future Teachers. *Maria José Latorre-Medina, FACULTY OF EDUCATION, ECONOMY, AND TECHNOLOGY OF CEUTA, UNIVERSITY OF GRANADA; Purificación Pérez-García, University of Granada*

15.010. Division K - Section 03: Teachers' Lives, Identities, and Journeys Virtual Poster Session.

Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

How Social Support Cultivates Teacher Digital Resilience? A Serial Mediation Analysis Based on Social Cognitive Theory. *Mingyu Wang, Hangzhou Normal University; Jing Wang, Hangzhou Normal University; Wenjing Zeng, Hangzhou Normal University*

Becoming Teachers at the Margins: Local Teacher Identity in Chinese Internationalized Schools(CIS). *XIAOLU BAI, University College London - IOE*

Social Justice Teacher Preparation: Throughlines Across University, Teacher Residency, and First Year in the Classroom. *Cori Salmerón, Georgia State University*
Challenges and Social Stigma of Male Gay and Transgender Foreign Teachers: A Qualitative Study. *Luis Miguel Dos Santos, Hong Kong Shue Yan University, Hong Kong; Litong QI, Hong Kong Shue Yan University; Hongyan Wang, Binghamton University - SUNY; Ying Li, Binghamton University - SUNY*

Teacher Vitality and its Generative Mechanism: A Key Issue in Building a High-quality Education System in China. *Nan Hao, Zhengzhou University; Tianqi Cao, Zhengzhou University*

15.010. Division K - Section 04: Foundations of Teaching and Teacher Education for Socio-Cultural, Racial, and Intersecting Minoritized Identities Virtual Poster Session.

Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Feminist Pedagogy in Instructional Design: A Content Analysis of the Journal of Applied Instructional Design. *Melissa Baysingar, Harper College*

Resisting Erasure: Racialized Teacher Candidates Rewriting the Future of Teacher Education. *Wenefe Capili-Balbalin, University of Ottawa*

Unforgetting to Imagine: Pre-service Teachers Use Photovoice to Envision Equitable Education. *Perla Barbosa, Salem State University; Priscila Leal, University of Hawaii - Manoa*

Enabling Transgressions: A Content Analysis of Racial Literacy Development Through Pre-Service Teachers' Reflective Journals. *Salandra Grice-Johnson, Sam Houston State University; Alexis M. Terry, American University*

Fostering Social-Emotional Learning in Teacher Education: Experiences from a Novel culturally adapted SEL Course. *Eman Abu-Hanna Nahhas, Oranim Academic College of Education and Gordon College; Hanadi Abu Ahmad, Beit Berl College-Israel*

15.010. Division K - Section 05: Pre-Service Teacher Coursework and Clinical Practice Virtual Poster Session.

Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Ethical Formation in the Practicum: Mentoring Pre-service Teachers in the Face of Contemporary Educational

Challenges. *Laia Lluch Molins, Universitat Oberta de Catalunya; Eduard Masdeu-Yélamos, Universitat Oberta de Catalunya*

Understanding Secondary ELA Pre-Service Teachers' Curricular Experiences: Insights from Clinical Placements in Diverse School Contexts. *Jessie O'Brien-Sheats, Lehigh University; Brook Sawyer, Lehigh University*

A Pilot Study of Phase-Specific Feedback Loops and Interventions in an Elementary Teacher Program. *Brittany M. Adams, University of Alabama; Cortney Dilgard, University of Alabama; Amanda Cramer, University of Alabama; Jennifer Pate, University of Alabama*

Profiling Pre-service Teachers in Blended Learning: A Dual-Dimensional Framework Integrating Behavioral Engagement and Dispositional Readiness. *jing wang, 华东师范大学*

Beyond the Fertile Paradox: Preservice Teachers' Steps Past Awareness to Action Against Injustice. *Eleni Duret, San Jose State University; Gena Merliss, Nazareth University*

Collaborative Lesson Design Between Pre-Service Mathematics Teachers and AI: A Mixed-Method Study. *rui zhao, east china normal university*

Expansive Framing as a Pathway for Fostering Transfer of Teacher Learning to Diverse Contexts. *Tripp Harris, University of South Carolina*

15.010. Division K - Section 06: In-Service Teacher Professional Development Virtual Poster Session.

Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Empowering Teachers: An Empirical Study on the Digital competency of Early Childhood Teachers in China. *Shiduo Wang, East China Normal University; Yutong Li, University College London - IOE*

Bridging the Gap Between Teacher Professional Development and Classroom Practice: An Equity-Driven, Collaborative Approach. *Salima Dhanani, Florida International University*

Exploring Factors Influencing Play-Based Learning in Supporting Elementary School Students' Social-Emotional Development from the Perspectives of Teachers. *Vy Van Dao, University of Social Sciences and Humanities-Vietnam National University HCM*

Sustainability in Professional Learning Communities: Historical Insights and Future Strategies. *Chinyere I Odia, University of North Texas; Sukai Durosimi, East Fort Worth Montessori Academy*

Investigating K-12 Teachers' Perception of Incorporating Generative AI into Students' Tasks. *Gyeongri Kim, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Peter Samuelson Wardrip, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Mapping the Journey to Exceptional Schooling for Multilingual Learners. *Naomi Flynn, University of Reading; Annela*

Teemant, Indiana University - Indianapolis

Context-Sensitive AI Chatbots for Scalable Teacher Professional Development: A Mixed-Methods Evaluation in Austrian Higher Education. *Thomas Leitgeb, University of Education Burgenland; Michael Leitgeb, University College Of Teacher Education Burgenland*

Examining Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) Among In-Service Secondary Teachers in Taiwan: Evidence From a Pilot Survey Study. *Chin-Yi Huang, Indiana University of Pennsylvania; Julie Winneur Ankrum, Indiana University of Pennsylvania*

15.010. Division K - Section 07: Teacher Educator Initial and Ongoing Development Virtual Poster Session.

Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Dismantling the Ivory Tower: The Positioning of "The University" on a Student Teaching Triad. *Diana Murtaugh, Binghamton University - SUNY*

When Technology Meets Emotion: A Study on University Teachers' Caring Behaviors in Online Teaching. *诗如王, 华中科技大学; 帅龙李, Central China Normal University*

GenAI in STEM Teacher Education: Investigating the Tensions and Emerging Possibilities of Adoption and Use. *Yvonne Franco, University of Tampa; Ruthmae Sears, University of South Florida; Stephanie A. Arthur, University of South Florida; Sandra Vernon-Jackson, University of South Florida*

15.010. Division K - Section 08: Teacher Recruitment, Induction, and Mentoring Virtual Poster Session.

Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Reimagining Mentorship in Language Teacher Education: A Relation-Centered Transpositional Framework and a TEAM Practice Model. *Huili Hong, Vanderbilt University; Li Wei, UCL Institute of Education*

15.010. Division K - Section 09: Innovative Design and Models for Teaching and Teacher Education Virtual Poster Session.

Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

From Amnesia to Agency: Reclaiming History for Justice-

Oriented Educational Futures. *Tara Ratnam, Independent Researcher*

Instructional Agency in the Digital Era: Mapping Teacher Beliefs, Development, and Technology Use. *Suyoun Kim, Korea University; Hyejeong Lee, University of Texas - San Antonio*

Drifting in the Library: Leading Students to Unexpected Texts Through a Situation. *Christina Jones, Education Library; Micaela Deogracias, Indiana University; Gustave J. Weltsek, Indiana University*

Empowering Educators: Teachers' Perspectives on Generative AI in Multimodal Digital Design Education. *Youwen Shi, The Chinese University of Hong Kong*

Centering Cultural Wealth: A Case Study of Refugee Girls' Education at Global Village Project. *Sarah S. Williams, University of North Georgia; Genevieve Gooley, Western Governors University*

How Secondary English Teachers Integrate AI-Guided Chatbots in Writing Feedback: Insights from Activity Theory. *Yuan Yao, Hong Kong Polytechnic University; Xinhua Zhu, Hong Kong Polytechnic University; Longhai Xiao, Zhejiang University; Hongbiao Yin, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Qi Lu, The Chinese University of Hong Kong*

Innovative and Intentional by Design: A Global Teacher Education Model Honoring Histories and Cultivating Futures. *Fatima Hasan Bailey, Sharjah Education Academy*

Future-Oriented Reflection in Simulation-Based Learning: A Freirean Lens on Teacher Development Across Modalities. *Orna Levin, Achva Academic College; Heidi Flavian, Achva Academic College*

15.010. Division L - Section 1: Governance, Politics, and Legal Issues Virtual Poster Session. Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Historic Parallels and Future Risks: Explaining Ohio's Governance Shift with Punctuated Equilibrium Theory. *Helen Buck-Pavlick, The Ohio State University; Ann M. Allen, The Ohio State University*

15.010. Division L - Section 4: Social, Political, and Cultural Contexts Virtual Poster Session. Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Research Culture in Georgian University and Its Role in the Development of Doctoral Education. *Tatia Kalandadze, ilia state university*

Bullying Constructs and Manifestations: A Comparative Study of Japan and the US. *Yurika Doi, Grinnell College*

A Human Rights-Based Framework for Trauma-Informed Pedagogy: Advancing Educational Access and Equity. *Stephani Nummelin, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Rohan Tapiawala, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*

15.010. Division L - Section 6: Social Policy, Inequality, and Student Outcomes Virtual Poster Session. Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Education, Inequality and Teenage Pregnancy in England: Policy Lessons for Equitable Support. *Yingxiang Chen, University of Bath; Liang Yuitan, Shenzhen Senior High School (Group) North Campus*

Why are Rural Students Absent from School? Evidence from West Virginia. *Michael A. Gottfried, University of Pennsylvania; Erin Gill, University of Pennsylvania; Stephen Colby Woods, University of Pennsylvania*

Reimagining Civic Literacy: A Comparative Study of Hong Kong's Liberal Studies Reform and U.S. Social Studies Standards. *Yunlu Wang, Georgia State University*

15.010. Division L - Section 7: Policy Implementation, Analysis, and Impact Virtual Poster Session. Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Improving Literacy Instruction at Scale: State Reading Policy Implementation and Capacity Building in Small and Rural Schools. *Sarah J Zuckerman, University of Nebraska - Lincoln; Michael Hebert, University of California - Irvine; Pamela Bazis, University of Nebraska - Lincoln; Sara Wing, University of Nebraska - Lincoln; Janet Bohaty, University of Nebraska - Lincoln; Nathan Speer, University of Nebraska - Lincoln; Rachel E. Schachter, University of Illinois at Chicago; Marc Goodrich, Texas A&M University; Derek Rodgers, University of Iowa*

"What Works, for Whom, and Under What Conditions" in Implementing Improvement Science at Scale. *Ariel Tichmor-Wagner, Boston University; Elizabeth Barcay, Boston University; Rohan Arcot, Boston University; Leslie Camilo Sears, Boston University*

Belonging without a Place: A Critical Policy Analysis of First-Gen Dual Enrollment Supports. *Shelby Terral, University of Houston*

Educational Leaders Navigating AI: Policy Challenges and Opportunities in K-12 Implementation. *Juhee Kim, University of Idaho; Elizabeth Wargo, University of Idaho*

Investigate Differences in Policy Enactment between Chinese and England Higher Education Reforms. *Dandan Li, University of Bath*

Implementing Digital Curriculum Reform: Policy, Governance, and Equity in Large-Scale Educational Transformation.

Christina Chinas, Durham University

2030 Is Almost Here: A Holistic Approach of Measuring and Exploring the Progress of SDG4. *Zehorit Dadon Golan, Rutgers University; Wendy M. Purcell, Rutgers University*

Reassessing Graduate Program Evaluation in Brazil: A Critical Perspective on the CAPES System through the Sociology of Education. *Vanessa Cotta Silveira Machado, Universidade Federal de Ouro Preto; Jose Rubens Lima Jardimilino, Federal University of Ouro Preto*

The Effects of the No Child Left Behind Act on Native American Languages: A Case Study on Navajo Public Schools in Arizona. *Jiaheng Yu, Northern Arizona University*

15.010. International Relations Committee Virtual Poster

Session. International Relations Committee; Virtual iPresentation Only

Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Preservice Teacher Development through Transnational Reflective Practices: A Bildung- Oriented Approach. *Doris A. Kroiss, University of North Carolina - Greensboro; Wiebke J. Langer, University of Hamburg; Ye He, University of North Carolina - Greensboro*

15.010. SIG-Accreditation, Assessment, and Program Evaluation in Education Preparation Virtual Poster

Session. SIG-Accreditation, Assessment, and Program Evaluation in Education Preparation; Virtual iPresentation Only

Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

A Pilot Study Exploring Education Majors' Reasoning About P-12 Classroom Disparities. *Amber Janel Adgerson, University of North Dakota; Emma Pitt, Northeastern University; Rebecca Peretz-Lange, Vassar College; John D. Coley, Northeastern University*

15.010. SIG-Action Research Virtual Poster Session.

SIG-Action Research; Virtual iPresentation Only

Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Exploring Pedagogical Practices in STEM Higher Education: An Action Research Study. *Menaka Abraham, University of Washington - Tacoma; Meredith Wronowski, University of Dayton*

15.010. SIG-Adolescence and Youth Development Virtual

Poster Session. SIG-Adolescence and Youth Development; Virtual iPresentation Only

Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Classroom Dynamics and Deviant Behavior Among Junior High School Students: A Multi-level Analysis. *Siwei Xu; Tianzhe Chen, University of Cambridge; Jiarui Luo, The Hong Kong Polytechnic University; Tongmao Li, The University of Florida*

Comfort, Care, and Connection: A Qualitative Inquiry into Young Adolescents' Perspectives on Belonging in School. *Tonje Mari Molyneux, University of British Columbia; Anusha Kassan, University of British Columbia; Jenna D. Shapka, University of British Columbia; Eva Oberle, University of British Columbia*

The Sexual Health Awareness Scale: Development, Validation, and Initial Applications. *Ozlem Sener, Bartin University; Suleyman Kahraman, Beykent University*

15.010. SIG-Advanced Technologies for Learning Virtual Poster Session.

SIG-Advanced Technologies for Learning; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

AI-Supported Emotional Well-Being in Learning: A Review of Empirical Studies. *Run Wen, Xi'an Jiaotong-Liverpool University; Na Li, Xi'an Jiaotong-Liverpool University; Manolis Mavrikis, University College London*

15.010. SIG-Arts and Inquiry in the Visual and Performing Arts in Education Virtual Poster Session.

SIG-Arts and Inquiry in the Visual and Performing Arts in Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Unforgotten Practices, Future Possibilities: Puppetry, Pedagogy and the Integrated Arts. *Laura McEntee, Mary Immaculate College; Edmond Gubbins, Mary Immaculate College*

15.010. SIG-Arts and Learning Virtual Poster Session.

SIG-Arts and Learning; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Digital Leadership and ICT Competence Among Music Educators: Evidence from Chinese Universities. *Xingzhi Guan, UCSI University; Jing Cai, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia*

From Shared Histories to Divergent Futures: A Comparative Analysis of Music Curriculum Policy in China and South Korea. *ZITONG LI, Ulsan of university*

15.010. SIG-Arts-Based Educational Research Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Arts-Based Educational Research; Virtual iPresentation Only

Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Collaging Co-Mentorship: A Feminist Approach for Mentorship, Troubling Norms, and Imagining Otherwise. *Lucy E. Bailey, Oklahoma State University; Stacie L. Warner, Oklahoma State University; Lindsey Abernathy, Oklahoma State University*

Art-Based Research, Decoloniality, and Gender-Based Violence: Voices of Women Students from India. *Ruchi Saini, University of Central Florida*

Bridging Silos Through Dance Pedagogy: Integrating Biology, Geography, and Embodied Teaching in Graduate Education. *lilin chen, Beijing Normal University*

15.010. SIG-Asian Americans and Pacific Islanders in Education and Research Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Asian Americans and Pacific Islanders in Education and Research; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Examination of the Pygmalion Effect of the Filial Piety on Asian American Students. *Sham`ah Md-Yunus, Eastern Illinois University; Joohi Lee, University of Texas - Arlington*

Bridging Worlds Through Literacy: A Culturally Sustaining Book Club for Korean Immigrant Parents and Korean American Children. *Jiyeong Joann Yi, Iowa State University; Constance C. Beecher, Iowa State University; Kunhui Kim, Iowa State University*

15.010. SIG-Bilingual Education Research Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Bilingual Education Research; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Co-Designing Justice-Oriented ESL Curricula: A Humanizing Approach to Research-Practice Partnerships. *Marisol Masso, Michigan State University*

ARCS-iLearn : An AI Agent-Based Vocabulary Learning Framework Grounded in ARCS Motivation Theory. *Yuxi Zhang, central china normal university; jianping huang, Beijing Normal University*

15.010. SIG-Biographical and Documentary Research Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Biographical and Documentary Research; Virtual iPresentation Only

Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Education as Liberation : Biography and Freedom in the Lives of Krishnamurti, Tagore and Gandhi. *Raji Swaminathan, University of Wisconsin - Milwaukee*

Life Writing, Embodiment, and Becoming: The Body as Pedagogy. *Amanda Kingston, Syracuse University; Stacie L. Warner, Oklahoma State University; Lindsey Abernathy, Oklahoma State University; Lucy E. Bailey, Oklahoma State University*

From Forgotten to Remembered: Using Oral Histories to Reclaim Rural BIPOC Educational Experiences through a Black Feminist-Womanist Lens. *Alexis Grant-Panting, Texas Woman's University*

Four Poetic Inquirers in Ancient China: Lu Ji, Liu Xie, Zhong Rong, and Tao Yuanming. *Botao Wu, University of British Columbia*

Auto/biographical Strategies of Women's Basketball Coaches as Educators. *Thalia Mulvihill, Ball State University*

15.010. SIG-Bourdieu in Educational Research Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Bourdieu in Educational Research; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

'By Chance' or 'by Choice'? A Bourdieusian Study of Graduates from Elite Universities as Schoolteachers. *Ruoxin Wang, University of South Australia; Guanglun Michael Mu, University of South Australia*

15.010. SIG-Brain, Neurosciences and Education Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Brain, Neurosciences and Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Emotional Neural Choreography: Parent-Child Brain Synchrony During Valenced Interactions. *Yihui Wang, Shanghai Normal University; Yihan Zhang, University of Macau; Lidian Huang, University of Macau; Juan Zhang, University of Macau*

Gaze, Language, and Attention: Demonstrative Use and Joint Attention in High Functioning Autism Spectrum. *Alaz Aydn, Middle East Technical University; Murat Perit Cakir, Middle East Technical University*

15.010. SIG-Career & Technical Education and Workplace Learning Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Career & Technical Education and Workplace Learning; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Collaborative Problem-Solving and Online Self-Efficacy in Technical and Vocational Higher Education: A Regression Tree Analysis. *Gonzalo Salas, Universidad de Chile; Daniela Edith Luengo-Aravena, Spencer Foundation*

Reimagining Teacher Leadership: Bridging Leadership Gaps with Competency-Based Digital Apprenticeships. *Matthew Bornak, Pennsylvania State University*

15.010. SIG-Caribbean and African Studies in Education Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Caribbean and African Studies in Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

A Socio-Cultural Reconceptualization of African History Through Literature and Historiography. *Oladipupo Adedamola Ogunfeibo, University of British Columbia*

Learning Management Systems in Under-Resourced Settings: Insights from Nigerian Private Primary and Secondary Schools. *Ijeoma Aboaja, Ottawa University*

15.010. SIG-Cognition and Assessment Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Cognition and Assessment; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Understanding How Students Learn from Multiple Sources: A Latent Variable Approach to Assessing Comprehension. *Zhaocheng Wu, Mississippi State University; Andrew Potter, Arizona State University; Danielle S. McNamara, Arizona State University*

Psychometrics Oversights: A Systematic Literature Review of Reliability, Validation and Fairness in Reading Self-Concept Measurements. *Onur Ramazan, University of Hong Kong; Robert W. Danielson, Washington State University - Spokane; Shenghai Dai, Washington State University; Chad M. Gotch, Washington State University*

15.010. SIG-Computer and Internet Application in Education Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Computer and Internet Application in Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Design Mode from the Start: Co-constructed futures through distributed epistemic agency. *Robert Huang, University of Toronto*

Enhance College Students' Argumentation Skills and Critical Thinking through ChatGPT-assisted In-class Debates. *Jiateng Zhou, Beijing Normal University; Yifei Diao, Central China Normal University; Jiawen Gou, Beijing Normal University; Ziyi Li, University of Cambridge; Wei Gao, Central China Normal University*

Pre-service Teachers' Knowledge Construction from Supported Online Inquiry: Evidence from Tagclouds. *Ying Xie, Northern Illinois University; Shu-yuan Lin, Idaho State University*

15.010. SIG-Critical Educators for Social Justice Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Critical Educators for Social Justice; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Seeds of Resistance: From Linguistic Wounds to Pedagogical Advocacy. *Leticia de la Garza, University of Central Arkansas*

Chalk, Codes, and Community: Reimagining Public Spaces for Equity and Multilingual Belonging. *Robert Niewiadomski, Fordham University*

15.010. SIG-Critical Examination of Race, Ethnicity, Class and Gender in Education Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Critical Examination of Race, Ethnicity, Class and Gender in Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Navigating Belonging: Minoritized Educators' Experiences of Inclusiveness in Schools. *Dilek Kayaalp, University of North Florida; Madalina F. Tanase, University of North Florida*

Invisible Structures, Visible Struggles: Intersectional Barriers Faced by Black Female Students with Disabilities. *ruiwen song, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia*

Can Racial Bias in Teachers' Decisions Be Reduced? Evidence from a Survey Experiment in French Middle Schools. *Charlotte CORCHETE, Sciences Po Paris*

Deconstructing and Reframing 'Azad Khayal Aurat': Women's Identity in Indian Higher Education. *Esra Nizami, University of Massachusetts - Amherst*

Positive Black Racial Identity and Post-Secondary Success among Black males. *Beverly-Jean Daniel, Toronto Metropolitan University; Alana C. Butler, Queen's University - Kingston*

15.010. SIG-Critical Peace Education Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Critical Peace Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Pedagogies of Refusal: How Gazan Educators Resist the Collapse of Higher Education During War. *Stephanie Robinson, University of North Texas*

15.010. SIG-Critical Posthuman and Postfoundational Studies in Education Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Critical

Posthuman and Postfoundational Studies in Education;
Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

The Rhizomatic Learning Paths in Becoming Post Qualitative Inquiry Researcher. *Aida Kairienė, Klaipėda university*
From "千人一声" to Posthuman Polyphony: Unforgetting Histories, Assembling Futures in Chinese Music Education. *Yaxin Li, University of Cambridge*

15.010. SIG-Decolonial, Postcolonial, and Anti-Colonial Studies in Education Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Decolonial, Postcolonial, and Anti-Colonial Studies in Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Youth, Museums, and Ownership of the Past—Reimagining Education Through the Java Man and Repatriation. *Joel E. Berends, Michigan State University*

15.010. SIG-Democratic Citizenship in Education Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Democratic Citizenship in Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Universities as Civic Ecologies: A Quantitative Study of Institutional Logics and Civic Engagement Predictors. *Ainslee Jacgdish Preciado, University of California - Los Angeles*

15.010. SIG-Design and Technology Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Design and Technology; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Enhancing Instructor Self-Efficacy Through AI Training in Higher Education. *Amani Itani, University of Houston; Dina Shouman, Lebanese International University*
Gamified Storytelling App for Medical English: A Mixed-Methods Design and Impact Evaluation. *Zahra Zolfaghari, Shiraz University - Iran; Shiraz University of Medical Sciences; Zahra karimian, Shiraz Ununiversity of Medical Sciences; nahid Zarifsaniey., Shiraz Ununiversity of medical sciences; amiryosuf farahmandi, Shiraz Ununiversity of medical sciences*

15.010. SIG-Disability Studies in Education Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Disability Studies in Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to

3:00pm

Participant:

Centering Disabled Students' Evaluation of Universal Design for Learning Pedagogy: An Innovative Teaching Project. *Molly McKeon, University of Colorado - Denver*

15.010. SIG-Early Education and Child Development Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Early Education and Child Development; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Gender-Specific Parental Influences on Neural Pathways of Children's Emotion Regulation. *Lidian Huang, University of Macau; Yihui Wang, Shanghai Normal University; Yihan Zhang, University of Macau; Juan Zhang, University of Macau*

Exploring the Role of Spanish Classroom Characteristics for Head Start Children's Academic Outcomes. *Ashley Diane Boros, The Ohio State University; Ji Young Choi, The Ohio State University*

Gentrification and Universal Pre-K: Examining Equity and Access in a South Boston Childcare Center. *Da Hei Ku, University of Massachusetts - Boston*

The Differential Impact of Pre-K on Homeless, Low-Income, and Non-Disadvantaged Children. *Travis S. Wright, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Scoping Review: Early Math Acquisition in Myanmar vs. China and the U.S. *Khin Aye Chan Thein, The Education University of Hong Kong; Yi Shen, The Education University of Hong Kong; Hui Li, The Education University of Hong Kong*

15.010. SIG-Educational Change Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Educational Change; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

A Professional Development to Support Upper-Elementary Teachers' Self-Efficacy to Implement Number Talks. *Kiera Kulaga, Monmouth University; Vecihi Serbay Zambak, Monmouth University*

Understanding COVID-19 Learning Loss: A Global Scoping Review of Standardized Test Outcomes for Grades 1–12. *Naichen Zhao, University of Denver*

15.010. SIG-Environmental Education Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Environmental Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

When Nature Didn't Cooperate: Children's Perspectives on a Failed Conservation Project. *Adiv Gal, Kibbutzim College*
Unheard Climate Voices: Indigenous Bedouin Youth at the

Crossroads of Place, Climate Change, and Justice. *Shaima Alokbe, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev; Orit Ben-Zvi Assaraf, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev*

Between Hope and Despair: Holistic and Interdisciplinary Climate Change Education for Teacher Trainees. *Netta Baryosef-Paz, Kibbutzim College; Dafna Gan, The Open University of Israel*

The Unexplored Relationships Between Forest Schools and Climate Change: The Parental Perspective. *Moriya Netzer, University of Haifa; Dafna Gan, The Open University of Israel; Ofira Ayalon, University of Haifa*

From Intention to Impact: Pre-Service Visions of Student Agency in Climate and Sustainability Education. *Dilraba Anayatova, Arizona State University; Andrea E. Weinberg, Arizona State University; Michelle Jordan, Arizona State University; Nicole Oster, Arizona State University*

The Role of Urban Intentional Community in Advancing Environmental Sustainability Education. *Shoshan Barkan-Eran, Hakibbutzim College of Education; Dafna Gan, The Open University of Israel*

Examining Ontario's Pre- and In-service Elementary Teachers' Knowledge about Climate Change and Climate Change Education. *Shiva Javanmardi, Western University; Anton Puvirajah, Western University*

Non-Formal Educators' Use of Artificial Intelligence in Environmental Education. *Yue Li, University of Florida; Megan Ennes, University of Florida; Jaehyun Ahn, University of Florida*

15.010. SIG-Experiential Education and Community Engagement: Scholarship and Practice Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Experiential Education and Community Engagement: Scholarship and Practice; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Teaching with Place: Developing Preservice Teacher Identity Through Outdoor Learning and Reflection. *Verdah Rehan, Clemson University; Steph N. Dean, George Mason University*

15.010. SIG-Faculty Teaching, Evaluation, and Development Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Faculty Teaching, Evaluation, and Development; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Reigniting Mid-Career Scholarship: A Faculty-Led Writing Boot Camp Grounded in Self-Determination Theory. *Jackie HeeYoung Kim, Georgia Southern University; Tracy Linderholm, University of North Carolina - Wilmington; E. Anthony Muhammad, Georgia Southern University; Antonio P. Gutierrez de Blume, Georgia Southern University*

Bridging the Skills Gap: Reimagining Faculty Development Through Centers for Teaching and Learning. *Nizar Bitar, The Max Stern Yezreel Valley College; Nitza Davidovich, Ariel University*

15.010. SIG-Family, School, Community Partnerships Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Family, School, Community Partnerships; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Partnerships among Families, Schools, and Communities for Multilingual Learners: Educator Aspirations and Promising Practices. *Ye He, University of North Carolina - Greensboro; Donather Daudi Magabe, University of North Carolina - Greensboro; Siphelele Qwabe, University of North Carolina - Greensboro; Tiffany Lee Smith Tovey, University of North Carolina - Greensboro; Bryan C. Hutchins, University of North Carolina - Greensboro*
Determinants of Governance Quality in Elementary and Secondary Education: Evidence from Seoul, South Korea. *Junghun Hwang, Seoul National University; Moonyoung Eom, Seoul National University*

15.010. SIG-Holistic Education Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Holistic Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Wisdom Illumination Education System (Secularized Pedagogy of the Five Illuminating Wisdoms): Framework for New Education. *yang ye, wuming culture media Ltd*

15.010. SIG-Indigenous Peoples of the Americas Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Indigenous Peoples of the Americas; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Towards Otherwise in Indigenous Education: Anishinaabe Beadwork Meets the Decolonial Imaginary. *Melissa Twance, Lakehead University*
Journeys Through STEM: Nurturing Indigenous Pathways of Persistence. *Nuria Jaumot-Pascual, TERC; Jessica M. Karch, TERC; Maria Ong, TERC; Jameson David Lopez, University of Arizona; Tiffany D. Smith, AISES*

15.010. SIG-Informal Learning Environment Research Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Informal Learning Environment Research; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Unlocking learner creativity through a robotics-enhanced story creation summer camp: A pilot study. *Qijie Vicky Cai, Towson University; Pei Ge, Towson University*

15.010. SIG-Instructional Technology Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Instructional Technology; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

- A Tale of Four Teachers: Integrating Desmos in High School Geometry After Professional Development. *Matthew Vazzana, Freehold Township High School; Vecihi Serbay Zambak, Monmouth University*
- Empirical Study of Stages of Concern and Influencing Factors in Chinese Rural Music Teachers' Multimedia Integration. *Xuejing Zhang, Universiti Sains Malaysia; Wan Ahmad Jaafar Wan Yahaya, Universiti Sains Malaysia*
- Leveraging Learning Analytics to Foster Self-Regulated Learning: A Multi-Semester Design-Based Research Study. *Kun Huang, University of Kentucky; Anita Lee-Post, University of Kentucky; Michael Stacy, University of Kentucky; Ryan Flores, University of Kentucky*
- When and How Students Engage with Augmented Generative AI During Mathematical Modeling Tasks. *Eunhye Flavin, Georgia Institute of Technology; Cristian Castaneda, Georgia State University*

15.010. SIG-International Studies Virtual Poster Session. SIG-International Studies; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

- Examining the Association Between Intercultural Dispositions and Global Competence Across Various Cultural Contexts. *Jinpeng Niu, Southwest University*
- Teachers' Training and Competence for Digital Mediation in Special Schools in Spain. *Esther Chiner, University of Alicante; Marcos Gómez-Puerta, University of Alicante; Cristina Miralles-Cardona, Universidad de Alicante; Maria Cristina Cardona, University of Alicante*
- Leveraging Online Research Experience for International University Admission: A Chinese Student Perspective. *Junjian Gao, Wenzhou-Kean University; Yolanda Sealey-Ruiz, Teachers College, Columbia University; Jinyi Ren, Wenzhou-Kean University*
- The Multifaceted Ethical Dilemmas of Postdoctoral Researchers: Toward Equitable Policies in International Mobility. *Yosef Katanov, Bar-Ilan University; Orly Shapira, Tel Aviv University; Annette Bamberger, Bar-Ilan University*

15.010. SIG-Language and Social Processes Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Language and Social Processes; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to

3:00pm

Participant:

- Preservice Clinicians' Language Ideologies, Translanguaging Stance and Confidence to Work with Emergent Bilinguals. *Grace Lee, University of Houston; Monique Mills, University of Houston*

15.010. SIG-Latina/o/x Research Issues Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Latina/o/x Research Issues; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

- Social Media As A Supplemental Tool for Harm Reduction Education Among Queer Latine. *Benjamin Coronado, University of California - Santa Cruz; Betsy Centeno, University of California - Santa Cruz; Saskias Casanova, University of California - Santa Cruz*
- "That Full Circle Connection:" Mentoring Future Educators through Service-Learning at a Hispanic-Serving Institution. *Kathryn Nagrotsky, University of Connecticut - Stamford; Jenifer Gaitan, Teachers College, Columbia University; Alyssa Hadley Dunn, University of Connecticut; Tracy Sinclair, University of Connecticut; Kenya Marie Overton, University of Connecticut; Ashanti Hall, University of Connecticut*

15.010. SIG-Law and Education Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Law and Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

- Opportunities and Challenges for Addressing Teacher-to-Student Bullying after Taiwan's New Legislation: A Conflicting Rationalities Analysis. *Jhih-Syuan Lin, National Chung Hsing University; Mike Yuchuan Shen, National Chung Hsing University*

15.010. SIG-Leadership for School Improvement Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Leadership for School Improvement; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

- Development and Validation of an Instrument for Assessing Departmental Leadership in China. *Jia Zhang, Zhejiang University*
- From Bureaucracy to Belonging: Transforming School Leadership for Adaptive Education among Native Americans. *James N. Onukwu, Washington State University*
- Leadership Practices in Academically Successful Under-resourced Philippine Elementary Schools: A Qualitative Inquiry. *Ma Glenda Lopez Wui, Ateneo de Manila University; Enrique Nino P. Leviste, Ateneo de Manila University; Jessica Sandra R. Claudio, Ateneo de Manila*

University; *Rosselle Trishia M. Reyes, Ateneo de Manila University*

School Leaders' Perspectives on Developing Inclusive and Equitable Schools. *Angela Voutier, Brandon University*
Research synthesis of principal system leadership from its birth to 2024: A narrative approach. *Cheng Jin, The Education University of Hong Kong; Junjun Chen, Education University of Hong Kong; Wendan XU, The Education University of Hong Kong*

15.010. SIG-Learning and Teaching in Educational Leadership Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Learning and Teaching in Educational Leadership; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

(Re)Imagining Principal Preparation Through Praxis: Integrating Problem-Based Learning and Reflective Practice in Educational Leadership. *Rachel Anna Kamnkhwani-Kaulembe, Boise State University*

15.010. SIG-Learning Environments Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Learning Environments; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Are more screens better? A study of the effects of classroom screens on student attention and learning outcomes based on eye movement evidence. *Aixia Li, LUDONG UNIVERSITY; Lu Li, The University of Ludong; liyan yu, Ludong University; 子群 李, Ludong university*

Learning Through Making: Elementary Students' Perceptions of a STEM Makerspace Learning Environment. *Anthony George Timpano, American School in Taichung; Rachel Sarah Sheffield, Curtin University; Rekha Bhan Koul, Curtin University*

Unforgetting Static Histories: Educational Digital-Human Platform for Primary Online Programming Futures. *Hailiang Yang, East China Normal University; Hongji Deng, Beijing Normal University; Hao Zheng, East China Normal University; Wenxuan Zhang, East China Normal University; Weiyu Zhang, Beijing Normal University; Yonghe Wu, East China Normal University*

15.010. SIG-Learning Sciences Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Learning Sciences; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Characterizing Digging Deeper in Online Information Behavior. *Sky Galili, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev; Iris Tabak, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev*
Pedagogical Play in the Makery: Examining Puppet Use in an

Elementary School Makerspace. *Robert Daniel Wachtel Pronovost, Stanford University*

15.010. SIG-Lesson Study Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Lesson Study; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

From Lesson Study to Collaborative Growth: Dialogic Pathways for Equitable Teacher Professional Learning. *Christina Chinias, Durham University*

15.010. SIG-Measurement and Assessment in Higher Education Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Measurement and Assessment in Higher Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

From Diagnosis to Dialogue: A Knowledge-Augmented Framework for Generating Interpretable Feedback from Deep Knowledge Tracing. *Zhen Li, Central China Normal University; Chenxuan He, Central China Normal University*

15.010. SIG-Media, Culture, and Learning Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Media, Culture, and Learning; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Virtual World Environments And Intercultural Communication in Language Learning: A Research Synthesis. *Priscilla Tuffour, University of South Florida - Tampa; Sanghoon Park, University of South Florida*

15.010. SIG-Middle-Level Education Research Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Middle-Level Education Research; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Understanding School Belonging in the Middle Grades: A Multilevel Analysis of Predictors Among Young Adolescents. *Tonje Mari Molyneux, University of British Columbia; Jenna D. Shapka, University of British Columbia; Anusha Kassan, University of British Columbia; Eva Oberle, University of British Columbia*

15.010. SIG-Moral Development and Education Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Moral Development and Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

"What If She is Poor? What If She Looks Different From me?": Children's Integration of Race and Wealthy Status in Their Fair Distribution Decisions. *Jee Young Noh, Biola University; Kelly Min, Biola University*

15.010. SIG-Motivation in Education Virtual Poster Session.

SIG-Motivation in Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Minute by Minute: Unfolding Patterns of Parental Behaviors in Math Homework Help. *Jiawen Wu, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Luxin Zhang, Teachers College, Columbia University; Yinuo Jia, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Eva M. Pomerantz, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Validation of the Korean Motivational Regulation Strategies Scale for Non-Traditional Adult Learners In Online Distance Learning. *Heoncheol Yun, Hankyong National University; Sanghoon Park, University of South Florida; Yongho Won, Hanyang University; Sukjin Kwon, Gukje Cyber University*

15.010. SIG-Multicultural/Multiethnic Education: Theory, Research and Practice Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Multicultural/Multiethnic Education: Theory, Research and Practice; Virtual iPresentation Only

Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

We Speak to All Students: Portraying Teachers' Language of Inclusivity. *Thomas Salsbury, Washington State University; Jihee Im, Washington State University; Eugenie Mainake, Washington State University*

From Marginalisation to Belongingness: Language and Well-being for Inclusive Education in South African Schools. *Margaret Funke Omidire, University of Pretoria; Shauib Abolakale Muhammed, University of Pretoria*

15.010. SIG-Music Education Virtual Poster Session. SIG-

Music Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Forced Nomadism in Thin Air: Music Teachers' Socioecological Burnout in Tibet. *Yuqi LIN, University of Macau; Qizong Yue, Southwest University; Katy Jeong Cheng Ho Weatherly, University of Macau*

15.010. SIG-Narrative Research Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Narrative Research; Virtual iPresentation Only

Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Breaking the Loop: A Narrative Inquiry of an International PhD Graduate in Academia. *Jiaxuan Zong, University of Maryland*

15.010. SIG-Online Teaching and Learning Virtual Poster

Session. SIG-Online Teaching and Learning; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Examining Instructor Social Presence and Student Outcomes in Higher Education: A Meta-Analysis. *Jing Song, Purdue University; Alexander J. Bowman, Purdue University; Zhuo Zhang, Towson University; Adrie A. Koehler, Purdue University; Yukiko Maeda, Purdue University; Jennifer C. Richardson, Purdue University*

The Relationships Between Community of Inquiry, Academic Procrastination, And Achievement Among Non-Traditional Online Students. *Sanghoon Park, University of South Florida; Yongho Won, Hanyang University; Sukjin Kwon, Gukje Cyber University; Heoncheol Yun, Hankyong National University*

Towards Equitable Online Learning: Gender, SES, Prior Experience, and Digital Literacy in Rural China. *Fengjiao Liu, University of Bristol*

15.010. SIG-Paulo Freire Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Paulo

Freire; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Compassionate Pedagogy as Strategic Practice: Advancing Educational Equity Through Historical Memory and Future-Oriented Teaching. *Jaelyn K. Rivard, University of Southern Mississippi*

15.010. SIG-Philosophical Studies in Education Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Philosophical Studies in Education; Virtual

iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Revisiting Matthews's Criticism from the Perspective of Piaget's Genetic Epistemology. *Haoran Liu, East China Normal University*

15.010. SIG-Politics of Education Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Politics of Education; Virtual iPresentation Only

Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Insurgencies on the Discursive Plains: The End of the Concretized Myth of White Supremacy. *Ayan Abdulle,*

University of Toronto - OISE

From Disruption to Imitation: Rethinking Innovation in the Charter School Movement. *Robert Niewiadomski, Fordham University*

15.010. SIG-Problem-Based and Project-Based Learning

Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Problem-Based and Project-Based Learning; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Revising Cultural Heritage, Cultivating Creativity: Project-Based Learning in Inner Mongolia's Public Kindergartens. *Yuxin Zhang, University of Malaya; Yu Zhou, University of Manchester*

15.010. SIG-Qualitative Research Virtual Poster Session.

SIG-Qualitative Research; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Confucian embodied knowing: Implications for reenvisioning qualitative methodologies. *Zitong Wei, China Women's University*

Words Speak for Themselves – Advocating for the Use of Documentary Data. *Dino Sossi, NYU, CUNY, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Unforgetting and Reimagining Belonging: A Duoethnography of International Faculty in a Midwestern PWI. *Somanita Kheang, Ball State University; Regina J. Giraldo-Garcia, Ball State University; Michael Takafor Ndeanu, Ball State University*

Human-AI Collaboration in Reflexive Thematic Analysis: A Case Study. *Yao Yang, Purdue University; Daniel Carpenter, Purdue University; Katie H Dufault, Purdue University; Craig Johnson, Purdue University; Anne Weiss, Purdue University*

15.010. SIG-Rasch Measurement Virtual Poster Session.

SIG-Rasch Measurement; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Does Answer Option Positioning Lead to DIF in Reading Comprehension? An Analysis with Parametric Logistic Item Response Theory Model Trees. *Farshad Effatpanah Hesari, Technical University of Dortmund; Islamic Azad University, Mashhad Branch*

A Rasch Analysis of the Couples Satisfaction Index. *Colette A Norgard, University of Colorado - Denver; Tom Su, University of Colorado - Denver*

15.010. SIG-Research in Mathematics Education Virtual

Poster Session. SIG-Research in Mathematics Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Portrayal of Female and Male Mathematicians in Theatrical Plays. *Emma LaPlace, Teachers College, Columbia University; Irina Lyublinskaya, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Psychometric Validation and Exploratory Path Analysis of the Chinese Math Attitudes Scale: A Single-Sample Study. *Run Wen, Xi'an Jiaotong-Liverpool University; Wenmin Zhao, University of Saint Joseph*

Avoiding a New Math War: Harmonizing Tensions Between Mathematics Education and Special Education Over Disability. *Thomas E. Ricks, Louisiana State University*

How do math anxiety, parent involvement, and academic self-concept impact adolescent math achievement? *Anna Levy, Fordham University; Yi Ding, Fordham University*

15.010. SIG-Rural Education Virtual Poster Session.

SIG-Rural Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Navigating Family-School Relationships in Rural Communities: A Scoping Review. *Abigail Stephan, Clemson University; Nora D. Hochstetter, Clemson University; Itunu Olaniran Akande, Clemson University; Verdah Rehan, Clemson University; Virginia Clark, Clemson University; Faiza M. Jamil, Clemson University*

15.010. SIG-School Community, Climate, and Culture Virtual

Poster Session. SIG-School Community, Climate, and Culture; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Reimagining School Belonging Through the Eyes of Young Adolescents: A Mixed Methods Inquiry. *Tonje Mari Molyneux, University of British Columbia; Jenna D. Shapka, University of British Columbia; Anusha Kassan, University of British Columbia; Eva Oberle, University of British Columbia*

Measuring School Climate Through Parents' Eyes: Scale Adaptation and Validation. *Louise Clément, Université Laval; Caterina Mamprin, Université de Montréal; Patricia Vohl, Université Laval; Marie-Christine Rivest, Université du Québec en Outaouais; Marie-Michèle Roy, Université de Moncton; Romane Gauvreau, Université Laval*

15.010. SIG-Science Teaching and Learning Virtual Poster

Session. SIG-Science Teaching and Learning; Virtual iPresentation Only

Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

A Micro-Level Discourse-Based Description of Modeling-Based Learning in Kindergarten Science. *Loucas T. Louca, European University Cyprus; Melina Xen, Ministry of Education and Culture, Cyprus*

15.010. SIG-Sociology of Education Virtual Poster Session.

SIG-Sociology of Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Effects of Employment Support Program in Vocational High Schools in South Korea on Labor-Market Outcomes. *Mina Je, Korean Educational Development Institute(prior)*

15.010. SIG-Special and Inclusive Education Research Virtual Poster Session.

SIG-Special and Inclusive Education Research; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Providing Services to All Students: Examining Teacher Awareness to Support LGBTQ+ Students with Disabilities. *Joseph A. Hogan, Kean University*

AAC Communication Partners' Knowledge of Abuse-Related Vocabulary Organization on AAC Devices. *Sarah Monaco, The College of New Jersey*

Inclusion of adults with Intellectual Development Disability in educational programs. *Heidi Flavian, Achva Academic College*

15.010. SIG-Stress, Coping, and Resilience Virtual Poster Session.

SIG-Stress, Coping, and Resilience; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Individual and Contextual Factors Attributing to Teacher Stress Based on Academic Setting and Years of Experience. *Parul Acharya, Columbus State University; Lisa Lashley Freeman, Bibb County School District, Georgia*

School Principals Under Pressure: Mental Load, Job Autonomy, and Retention. *Marie-Christine Rivest, Université du Québec en Outaouais; Louise Clément, Université Laval*

A conceptual framework of principal resilience: Narrative review from 2005 to 2024 (Poster 55). *Wendan XU, The Education University of Hong Kong; Junjun Chen, Education University of Hong Kong; Cheng Jin, The Education University of Hong Kong*

15.010. SIG-Studying and Self-Regulated Learning Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Studying and Self-Regulated Learning; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Phase-Specific Effects of AI in Self-Regulated Learning: A Meta-Analysis of a Decade of Interventions. *Jun Xu, East China Normal University; Yuying Luo, Shanghai University; Chengliang Wang, Australian Catholic University; Hao Zheng, East China Normal University; Yonghe Wu, East China Normal University*

15.010. SIG-Supervision and Instructional Leadership Virtual Poster Session.

SIG-Supervision and Instructional Leadership; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

A (Very) Exploratory Study of Practicum Interactions and Their Impact on Teaching Performance. *Jamie H. Hamblin, Southern Utah University; Abbey Judd, Southern Utah University; William J. Davis, Southern Utah University*

15.010. SIG-Survey Research in Education Virtual Poster Session.

SIG-Survey Research in Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Exploring Student Perspectives on Instructional Evaluations: A Qualitative Study of SPoI Participation and Feedback. *Elizabeth Templeton, Florida Gulf Coast University; Jenny Kerzetski, School District of Lee County; Jingshun Zhang, Florida Gulf Coast University*

15.010. SIG-Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis Virtual Poster Session.

SIG-Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Rethinking School-Based Substance Use Interventions: An Overview of Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analysis through Educational and Public Health Lenses. *Emily Jenkins, University of British Columbia; Mohammad Karamouzian, University of Toronto; Tonje Mari Molyneux, University of British Columbia; Dana Dmytro, University of British Columbia*

Does Technology-Based Learning Environment Promote Students' Self-Regulated Learning? A Meta-Analysis of Two Decades of Empirical Research. *Yinuo Li, university of bristol*

The Impact of Project-Based Learning on Achievement in

Secondary Mathematics. *Angie Sostak, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

Exploring the influence of secure attachment on bullying behaviors. *Yihan Zhang, University of Macau; Yihui Wang, Shanghai Normal University; Juan Zhang, University of Macau*

15.010. SIG-Systems Thinking in Education Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Systems Thinking in Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Evaluating the Homological Reasoning Levels of Senior Pre-service Middle School Science Teachers Using System Scenarios. *Ulku Seher Budak, Bogazici University; Gaye Defne Ceyhan, Bogazici University*

15.010. SIG-Teachers Work/Teacher Unions Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Teachers Work/Teacher Unions; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Two Decades of Teacher Organizing in New Orleans: "We're On the Front Lines." *Riley Collins, University of California - Santa Cruz*

15.010. SIG-Technology as an Agent of Change in Teaching and Learning Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Technology as an Agent of Change in Teaching and Learning; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

A Multi-Modal Analysis: Young Children's Spatial Skills While Using Educational Robots. *Simge Cicek, Bogazici University; Duygu Umutlu, Bogazici University*
ICT Practices: Influence of ICT Preparedness, ICT Induction, and Teacher Self-Efficacy. *Chengcheng Li, The Open University of China; Shaoan Zhang, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Qingmin Shi, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*
Designing for Change: Integrating Generative AI into Pre-Service Literacy Pedagogy. *Shannon M. Kane, University of Maryland; Loren Jones, University of Maryland*
A Case for AI Literacy: Generated Images Reproducing Biases. *Matthew Duvall, University of Pennsylvania; Chen Wang, University of Pennsylvania*
A Systematic Review of Studies on the Use of Generative Artificial Intelligence Tools in PK-12 Education. *Lauren J. Woo, Arizona State University; Leanna Archambault, Arizona State University; Jered Borup, George Mason University*
Looking Beyond the Output: How Preservice Teachers Assess

the Instructional Value of AI-Generated Formative Tasks. *Molly Li, University of Delaware; Leigh Hibbard, University of Delaware; Rachel A. Karchmer-Klein, University of Delaware*

H5P and Chinese College Students' Second Language Learning Engagement. *Yu Bi, Nantong Institute of Technology; Run Wen, Xi'an Jiaotong-Liverpool University*

ChatGPT and Lesson Planning in Early Childhood Education: Insights from Early Childhood Educators in the U.S.

Saigeetha Jambunathan, New Jersey City University; J.D Jayaraman, New Jersey City University

Mathematical Rigor, Mastery Learning, and Growth Mindset: A Content Analysis of IXL and Khan Academy. *Shalom Labkovski, Township of Ocean Schools; Vecihi Serbay Zambak, Monmouth University*

15.010. SIG-Technology, Instruction, Cognition & Learning Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Technology, Instruction, Cognition & Learning; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Using Multi-Agent AI to Understand Cognitive Load and Emotional States in K-12 Math Learning. *Fan Zhang, University of Florida; Wanli Xing, University of Florida*
Unplugged Computational Thinking Activities and the Development of Primary Students' Self-Concept of Ability and Core Cognitive Skills: A Longitudinal Multi-Site Study in Austria. *Thomas Leitgeb, University of Education Burgenland; Wolfram Rollett, University of Oldenburg; Katja Scharenberg, Ludwig Maximilian University of Munich*
The Effects of SHAP Mechanism Disclosure on Trust in LLM Scoring Across Computational Thinking Levels. *Bingjie Zhang, The University of Hong Kong; Zhichun Liu, University of Hong Kong*
Beyond Single Scores: A Dual-Dimensional Assessment of Student Mastery in AI. *Zhen Li, Central China Normal University; Chenxuan He, Central China Normal University; Shangheng Du, East China Normal University*

15.010. SIG-Urban Learning, Teaching, and Research Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Urban Learning, Teaching, and Research; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Stories of Trauma Among Teachers in Urban Classrooms. *Ami Ladhawala, University of Missouri - Kansas City; Candace M. Schlein, University of Missouri - Kansas City*

15.010. Research on Giftedness, Creativity and Talent Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Research on Giftedness, Creativity and Talent; Virtual iPresentation Only

Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Latent Classes of Ideation. *Süreyya Yörük, Bogazici University; Sedat Sen, Harran University*

15.010. Division C - Learning and Instruction / Division C - Section 3b: Technology-Based Environments Virtual Poster Session. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Comparing the Effects of Intelligent Tutoring Systems and Traditional Instruction on Sight-Singing and Aural Skills. *TINGTING CHEN, Hunan International Economics University*

Navigating the Boundary: English Language Teachers' Identity Perceptions in the Age of Artificial Intelligence Integration. *Nizar Bitar, The Max Stern Yezreel Valley College; Roseanne Kheir Farraj, Max Stern Yezre'el Valley College; Aya Onallah, The Max Stern Yezreel Valley College*

Automating Meso-Level Classroom Analysis: An LLM-Based Approach Using the PTA Coding Framework. *Xiangfang Song, East China Normal University; Jingliang Kong, East China Normal University*

The Role of Complex Learning Interactions and Cognitive Load in Immersive Virtual Reality-based Chemistry Simulations. *Maral Karimi, University of Central Florida; Megan Wiedbusch, University of Central Florida; Cameron Marano, University of Central Florida; Annamarie Broshinan, University of Central Florida; Tara Brianna Delgado, University of Central Florida; Marta Sobocinski, University of Oulu; Natalie Blaize, University of Central Florida; Romina Jannotti, Trinity Preparatory School; Roger Azevedo, University of Central Florida*

15.010. Division C - Section 1d: Science Virtual Poster Session. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Exploring the Impact of STEM Education on Scientific Creativity and Reflective Thinking in Elementary Science Education. *Umran Atabas, Istanbul 29 Mayıs University; Gonul Sakiz, Marmara University*

Agency in the Climate Crisis: Reframing Science Education Through a Three-Lens Approach (Poster 4). *Giulia Tasquier, University of Bologna; Francesca Pongiglione, University Vita-Salute San Raffaele; Elena Claire Ricci, University of Verona*

15.010. Division E - Section 1: Counseling Virtual Poster

Session. Division E - Counseling and Human Development; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Unpacking beliefs about change and personal theories of change in counselors-in-training writing. *Beata M. Latawiec, Wichita State University; Jody Fiorini, Wichita State University; Jason Li, Wichita State University; Susan Bray, Wichita State University*

15.010. Social and Emotional Learning Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Social and Emotional Learning; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Understanding Misalignment Between Parents' and Children's Reports of Life Satisfaction. *Luofan Shu, Graduate Center - CUNY; Anastasiya A. Lipnevich, City University of New York*

15.010. Teaching History Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Teaching History; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Learning to Contextualize: Modelling and Teaching a Complex Skill in History Education. *Marc-Andre Ethier, Université de Montréal; Kevin Péloquin, University of Montréal; David Lefrancois, University of Quebec - Outaouais; René Salem, University of Montréal*

15.010. Critical Perspectives on Early Childhood Education Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Critical Perspectives on Early Childhood Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Worlds Away & Belly Aches: A Critical Content Analysis of Enclosure in Picturebooks (Poster 16). *Seneca Beth Miller, University of Arizona*

Unraveling the Colonial Illusion of Representation: Material Agency for Relational Ethics in Early Childhood Art Inquiry (Poster 12). *Hyewon Oh, Growing Place Ocean Park Early Childhood Education Center*

15.010. SIG-Graduate and Postdoctoral Education Across the Disciplines Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Graduate and Postdoctoral Education across the Disciplines; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Facilitating Doctoral Student Development: Insights from the Student-Supervisor Relationship and Its Impacts. *Yingxiu Li, The Education University of Hong Kong; Wendan XU, The Education University of Hong Kong; Junjun Chen, Education University of Hong Kong*

Examine Power Dynamic: Equity and Mentorship in Transnational Doctoral Supervision. *Cheng Cui, Xi'an Jiaotong-Liverpool University; Qian Wang, Xi'an Jiaotong-Liverpool University; Jeong Jin Yu, Xi'an Jiaotong-Liverpool University; Martin Gough, University of Liverpool; Rong Yan, Xi'an Jiaotong-Liverpool University*

15.010. Religion and Education Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Religion and Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Incorporating Dialogic Education and the Traditional Halaqah Model in UAE Primary Islamic Studies Classrooms. *Arwa Al Qassim, University of Cambridge*

15.010. Division J - Section 1: Student Learning and Development in College and Beyond Virtual Poster Session. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

"I Wasn't Given These Experiences for Just Myself": Black Undergraduate Women's Purpose Development as Resistance and Self-Preservation at a Predominantly White Institution. *Jayla Moody Marshall, North Carolina State University*

15.011. Division C Early Career Mentoring Seminar (Closed Session). Division C - Learning and Instruction; Workshop
Westin Bonaventure, Level 3, Santa Monica A; 7:45-11:15am

Chairs: *Heather Rogers Haverback, Towson University; Daniel Dinsmore, University of North Florida*

15.012. Division C Graduate Student Mentoring Program (Closed Session). Division C - Learning and Instruction; Workshop
Westin Bonaventure, Level 3, Santa Monica C; 7:45-11:15am

Chairs: *Sandra Graham, University of California - Los Angeles; April Z. Taylor, California State University - Northridge*

15.013. Division C Mentoring Sessions Meal Room(Closed Session). Division C - Learning and Instruction; Workshop
Westin Bonaventure, Level 3, Santa Monica B; 7:45-

11:15am

Chairs: *Imogen Herrick, University of Kansas; David Wakefield, California State University - Northridge*

15.014. Division C Youth Conference (Closed Session). Division C - Learning and Instruction; Workshop
Westin Bonaventure, Level 3, Santa Monica D; 7:45-11:15am

Chairs: *Imogen Herrick, University of Kansas; David Wakefield, California State University - Northridge; Michael A. Lawson, University of Alabama*

15.015. Self-Regulated Learning and Motivation in Technology-Enhanced Environments. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Los Feliz; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

From Clicks to Insights: Exploring SRL Behaviors Longitudinally using Institutional Data. *Heeryung Choi, University of Minnesota; Chris Steadman, University of Minnesota; Caitlin Mills, University of Minnesota; Panayiota Kendeou, University of Minnesota*

Generative AI Chatbots as Co-regulators: Enhancing Self-Regulated Learning Across Learner Personality Profiles. *Xiu-Yi Wu, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Thomas K.F. Chiu, The Chinese University of Hong Kong*

Investigating Costs Associated with K12 Students' Online Learning. *Franziska Bickel, North Carolina State University; Qiuqing Li, North Carolina State University; Nilloufar Bayati, North Carolina State University; Zaina Dali, North Carolina State University; Shiyan Jiang, North Carolina State University; Rebecca Ellis, The Concord Consortium; Jie Chao, The Concord Consortium*

Learning and Motivation in Synchronous and Asynchronous Online Education: A Meta-Analytic Review. *Andreas Gegenfurtner, University of Augsburg*

Motivational Effects of Annotations and Quizzes in a VR-Based Field Trip. *Carina Galler, Universität der Bundeswehr München; Maximilian Christian Fink, Universität der Bundeswehr München; Bianca Watzka, RWTH Aachen University; Bernhard M. Ertl, Universität der Bundeswehr München*

Chair: *Daryn Dever, University of Florida*

15.016. Identity, Efficacy, and Trajectory: Explorations Across the Professions. Division I - Education in the Professions; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 3; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Motivation, Self-Efficacy, Student Adjustment in Relation to Engineering Identity and Academic Achievement. *Anqi Zhang, Fordham University; Yi Ding, Fordham University; Yifan Wang, Fordham University; Qian Wang, Manhattan*

College

Forcing the Curve: Undergraduate Business Students' Reactions and Unintended Consequences. *Claire Boeck, University of Rochester; Annette Sieg, University of Michigan; Nikki Westphal, University of Michigan*

Intersections of Identity and Innovation: Findings on the Experiences of Successful Minority Professionals in Learning, Design, and Technology. *Shalene Evett Turner; Tutaleni I. Asino, Carnegie Mellon University*

No Scrubs: A Study of Nursing Applicant Trajectories after Rejection. *Jennifer A. Torgerson, College of Southern Nevada*

Chair: *Kadian McIntosh, University of Arizona*

Discussant: *James L Huff, University of Georgia*

15.017. Examining AI Perspectives and Usage in

Postsecondary Teaching. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum G; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Artificial Intelligence in Community Colleges: Reimagining Teaching, Ethics, and Faculty Work Toward Student Agency. *Aikebaier Nadila, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Faculty Perspectives on Generative AI: An Examination of Expectations, Policies, and Practices on Course Syllabi. *Rachel Eunjoon Um, New York University; Hui Soo Chae, New York University*

Student Voices on AI: Exploring Perspectives on Undergraduate Classroom Policies. *Jae-eun Russell, University of Iowa; Salim George, University of Iowa; Jeremy A Dietmeier, University of Iowa; Anna Smith, University of Iowa*

Navigating the AI Turn in Higher Education: Faculty Practices, Institutional Ecologies, and Policy Gaps. *Mojtaba Khajeloo, University of Memphis; Yu Wu, University of Memphis; Gina English Tillis, The University of Memphis*

Discussant: *Zhaochen Gu, University of Illinois at Chicago*

15.018. Navigating Transitions: Equity, Belonging, and the

First-Year Experience. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum F; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Between Expectations and Concerns: Indigenous Students Navigating the Transition to Higher Education in Colombia. *Ruth E. Cuasialpud-Canchala, University of Arizona; Jameson David Lopez, University of Arizona*

Bridging the Gap for Disadvantaged Students: How College Transition Program Influences Academic Performance through Readiness and Engagement. *Xin Gao, Shanghai Jiao Tong University; Ruitian Lin, Shanghai Jiao Tong*

University; Yuerong Tong, Shanghai Jiao Tong University; Tingting Zhang, Shanghai Jiao Tong University; Shuai Wang, Shanghai Jiao Tong University

How a First-Year Transition Program for FGLI Students Fosters College Belonging and Identity Development. *Rebecca Ann Lawrence, Northwestern University; Mesmin Destin, Northwestern University*

The Price of Access: How Marginalized Students Navigate Racialized Barriers in Financial Aid Processes. *Jaime Ramirez-Mendoza, University of California - Davis*

Chair: *Natasha A. Saelua, Texas State University*

Discussant: *Abbas Abbasov, University of Texas at El Paso*

15.019. Beyond the Hype: Teachers, GenAI, and the Human Factor. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education;

Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 2; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

A Systematic Review of Teachers' Roles and Social-Emotional Support in K-12 AI Research. *Jiayu Cheng, University of Pennsylvania; Chen Wang, University of Michigan; Bodong Chen, University of Pennsylvania*

Examining Teachers' Generative Artificial Intelligence Competencies and Impact Factors. *Lehong Shi, University of Georgia*

Framework for AI Professional Development: Insights from Needs and Challenges of K-12 Educators. *Rizwan Shaikh, Texas A&M University-Corpus Christi; Kimberly S. Reinhardt, Texas A&M University - Corpus Christi*

"It Still Needs a Human Touch": K-12 Teachers' Uses, Perceptions, and Ethical Concerns Around Generative AI. *Chelsey Bahlmann Bollinger, James Madison University; Sana H Jaf, James Madison University*

Teachers' Intentions Towards AI for Administrative Relief: A TOE-Enhanced TAM Lens. *Yifan Zhang, Beijing Normal University; Rongxia Zhuang, Beijing Normal University; Dejian Liu, Beijing Normal University*

Discussants: *Abdul-Qadir D. Islam, Teachers College, Columbia University; Doug Havard, Chapman University*

15.020. Centering Equity & Agency in Teacher Learning: Innovations & Tensions in Professional Development

Across Contexts. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 9; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Coaching as Assisting Teacher Agency within School-Based Teams to Enact Equitable Classroom Discussions. *Lois A. Yamauchi, University of Hawai'i at Manoa; E. Brook Chapman de Sousa, University of Hawai'i at Mānoa; Rebecca 'Ilima Ka'anehe, University of Hawai'i at Manoa; Jamie C. Simpson Steele, University of Hawai'i at Manoa;*

Bryant Jensen, Brigham Young University

Developing Equity-Centered Mathematics Practice: The Role of Facilitator Variability in Teacher Professional Learning. *Rachel Saperstein McClam, Johns Hopkins University*

Teaching without Preparation: PhD Graduates' Adaptation to School Teaching Through the Interplay between Structure and Agency. *Chujun Luo, Chinese University of Hong Kong*

There are no shortcuts: A mixed methods study of micro-credentials for Culturally Responsive Pedagogy. *Chris K. Chang-Bacon, University of Virginia; Russell Carlock, Albemarle County Public Schools; Abigail Akosua Amoako Kayser, James Madison University; Mandy Flores-Curley, University of Virginia; Maria Guzman Antelo, Rhode Island College; Nina R. Schoonover, University of Virginia; Ben Allen, University of Virginia*

The Role of Modality: How Resources Support Early Childhood Teachers' Equity-Oriented Professional Learning. *Anna Oliveri, Salve Regina University*

Chair: *Jennifer M. Collett, Lehman College - CUNY*

Discussant: *Brian Odiwuor, Syracuse University*

15.021. Drawing On Histories For the Futures of Culturally Responsive Teaching. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 7; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Mirrors and Windows: Reflective Practice and Culturally Responsive Pedagogy in Preservice Secondary Education. *Tiffany B. Robinson Young, Office of the Military - Department of Defense STARBASE High Sierra; Jafeth Sanchez, University of Nevada - Reno*

Prototype of Socio-Culturally Responsive Teaching Excellence: Insights from Award-Winning Educators. *Toyosi Stephen Adedara, Baylor University*

Influence of CRIOP (Culturally Responsive Instruction Observation Protocol) Family Indicators on the Math Achievement of English Language Learner (ELL) Students. *Jaylene Patterson, University of Kentucky; Olukemi Olubunmi Kolawole, University of Kentucky; Shannon O. Sampson, University of Kentucky*

The Power of Discretionary Spaces in Teaching: Connections Between Systemic Injustice and Everyday Practice. *Deborah Loewenberg Ball, University of Michigan; Darrius D. Robinson, University of Michigan*

Chair: *Marlinda Boxley, Bowie State University*

Discussant: *Imani Masters Goffney, University of Maryland*

15.022. Honoring, Unforgetting, and Humanizing Teacher Preparation: Acknowledging Complexity in the Process. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 8; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Complex Systems in Beginning Teacher Learning-Practice: A Literature Review. *Kathryn J. Strom, California State University - East Bay; Celina Salvador-Garcia, University Jaume I; Jennifer Ervin, University of Wisconsin - Eau Claire; Maverick Yunqiang Zhang, Hunter College - CUNY; Alexis Ozuna, California State University - East Bay; Kara Mitchell Viesca, University of Nebraska - Lincoln*

Honoring Preparation, Resisting Prescription: Toward Just and Humanizing Teacher Education. *Taylor Weber, University of Tennessee; Emily Holtz, University of Tennessee; Stephanie Michelle Moody, Towson University*

Before the First Lockdown: Rethinking Teacher Preparation for School Shootings. *Isabel Mavrides-Calderon, Barnard College*

Disrupting Spatial Narratives: Redlining, Place-Based Pedagogy, and Preservice Teacher Learning. *Crystal G Simmons, University of North Carolina - Wilmington; James Oigara, SUNY - College at Geneseo*

Supporting University Supervisors in their Understanding of Equity through Professional Learning Communities. *Lindsay J. Wexler, North Central College*

Discussant: *Jessica N. Hiltabidel, George Mason University*

15.023. Sense-Making in the Disciplines: Literacy Resource for Interrogating Past and Future As Teacher Pedagogical Tool. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Symposium

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 6; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Sense-Making in the Disciplines: Literacy Resource for Interrogating Past and Future As Teacher Pedagogical Tool. *Carol D. Lee, Northwestern University*

SenseMaker as a Tool for Literary Reasoning. *Yolanda J. Majors, Northwestern University*

The SMD Tool for Disciplinary Reasoning and Design for Identity Development: A Teachers View. *Leslie A. Russell, Northwestern University*

Shifting Mindsets: SenseMaker as a disciplinary literacies and reasoning. *Mariya Yukhymenko, California State University - Fresno*

Chair: *Elizabeth Birr Moje, University of Michigan*

Discussant: *Elizabeth Birr Moje, University of Michigan*

15.024. STEM Education and Culturally Sustaining Pedagogy: Envisioning New Horizons in Teacher Preparation for Student Liberation. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Symposium

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum I; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Expanding CSP Through Afro-Indigeneity and Pan-Disability: An Inclusive Equity STEM Interrogation. *Johana E. Thomas*

Zapata, Washington State University; Alexis Padilla, Independent Scholar

STEM Sin Fronteras: Bridging Culturally Sustaining Pedagogies, Chicana Feminist and DisCrit Perspectives in Third Space STEM Education for Latinx Youth. *Rachel G. Salas, University of Nevada - Reno; Lizeth I. Lizarraga, University of Texas at Austin*

CSP in STEM Teaching: Preparing the Next Generation through Ambitious Teaching in Mathematics and Science. *Karen L. Terrell, Loyola University Maryland; Karen Clark, Loyola University Maryland; Afra Ahmed Hersi, Loyola University Maryland; Stacy Williams, Loyola University Maryland; Qi Shi, Loyola University Maryland*

Advancing Culturally Responsive STEM Education: An Evidence-Based Framework for Latinx Student Success Through Monarch Butterfly Migration. *Maryam Saberi, University of Shiraz; Noushin Nouri, University of Texas - Rio Grande Valley*

A Heuristic Model for the Preparation of Culturally Sustaining Teachers of Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics. *Diane H. Silva Pimentel, Brown University; Indira Gil, Brown University*

Rightful Presence in Early Childhood STEM: Honoring Disability Culture through Professional Development. *Michele Stites, University of Maryland - Baltimore County; Hsiu-wen Yang, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Chih-Ing Lim, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Susan Sonnenschein, University of Maryland - Baltimore County; Megan Vihn, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Jonathan E. Singer, University of Maryland - Baltimore County; Besjane Krasniqi, University of Maryland - Baltimore County; Freya Kaur, University of Maryland - Baltimore County*

Chair: *Indira Gil, Brown University*

Discussant: *Karen L. Terrell, Loyola University Maryland*

15.025. Supporting Teachers to Engage in Meaningful Data Literacy and Data Science Practices Across Disciplines.

Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Structured Poster Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 515A; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

1. Data Doulas: Supporting Educators to Cultivate Data-Rich Instruction in STEM Classrooms (Poster 1). *Nicole Wong, WestEd; Leticia Perez, WestEd; Kirsten Daehler, WestEd*
2. Elementary Teachers' Self-efficacy and Interest in Teaching Data Science (Poster 2). *Danielle C. Herro, Clemson University; Jeremiah Nosakhare Akhigbe, Clemson University; Matthew J. Madison, University of Georgia*
3. Using Digital Tools to Support Elementary Teachers Development of Data Science Literacy (Poster 3). *Laura Shelton, University of Houston; Mandana Delavari, University of Houston; Travis Weiland, University of North*

Carolina - Charlotte; Caitlin Ireland, University of North Carolina - Charlotte

4. Supporting Critical Data Literacy Instruction in Social Studies Through Online PD and Resources (Poster 4). *Tamara L. Shreiner, Grand Valley State University; Bradford Dykes, Grand Valley State University*
5. Engaging Data Literacy through Active and Engaged Classroom Discourse Practices (Poster 5). *Kristy Brugar, University of Oklahoma; Julianna E. Lopez Kershen, University of Oklahoma*
6. "Not a Data Person" but Still Exploring: English Language Arts Teachers' Experiences in Teaching Data (Poster 6). *Nichole Nomura, University of Wyoming; Daniela Gamboa Zapatel, Stanford University; Victor R. Lee, Stanford University; Sarah Levine, Stanford University; Christine Bywater, Stanford University*
7. Seeing, Thinking, Wondering: Cultivating Data Literacy in Preschool with Primary Sources (Poster 7). *Ilene R. Berson, University of South Florida; Michael J. Berson, University of South Florida*
8. Designing at the Boundary: Exploring Teachers' Integration of Data Science and Mathematics (Poster 8). *Elizabeth Metts, Vanderbilt University; Kate Chapman; Ji Son, California State University - Los Angeles*
9. Pre-service Teachers' Evaluations of Ethics and Data Rights Across Individual, Communal, and Societal Layers (Poster 9). *Victoria L. Delaney, San Diego State University; Ryan Gabriel Aniceto, San Diego State University*

Chair: *Katherine M. Miller, Concord Consortium*

Discussant: *Michelle Hoda Wilkerson, University of California - Berkeley*

15.026. Gender Equity in STEM from a Comparative

Education Policy Perspective. Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 10; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

- Gender Equity in Higher Education Policy in Chile: Between Symbolic Inclusion and Structural Exclusion. *Francisca Beroiza-Valenzuela, Universidad de las Américas (UDLA), Chile; Daniela Véliz Calderón, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile*
- Mathematics Motivation, Achievement, and Gender Inequality in Social Institutions: Unpacking Gender Differences in STEM Career Expectations Across 81 Societies. *Wei Wu, Peking University; Yanan Zhang, Renmin University of China; Mi Wang, Nanjing Xiaozhuang University*
- Unequal access, equal outcomes? Gender differences in the relationship between university-led STEM program factors and undergraduates' career commitment in STEM. *Wei Wu, Peking University; Congbin Guo, Peking University*

Discussant: *Lina Safa, Pepperdine University*

SIG Sessions

15.027. From Margins to Models: Sustaining Heritage & Dual Language Education in Less Commonly Taught Languages. SIG-Bilingual Education Research; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304C;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

- Vietnamese American Educators Navigating Racial and Political Conflicts in Vietnamese DLBE Program. *Alisha Nguyen, Lesley University*
- Lub Zej Zog Project: HMoob Educators Coalitions' use of sib hlub si pa(a)b and participatory design research (re)claim linguistically and culturally sustaining education. *Jenna Cushing-Leubner, University of Wisconsin - Whitewater*
- "Nothing belongs to us": The Spatial Precarity of Heritage Language Education in Mainstream Public Schools. *Rima Elabdali, University of Tennessee*
- How Transnational Histories shape Educational Futures: Understanding Parental Ideologies and Parent-School Relations in DLBE Schooling. *Hina Ashraf, Georgetown University; Lourdes Ortega, Georgetown University*

Chair: *Alisha Nguyen, Lesley University*

Discussant: *Ester J. de Jong, University of Colorado - Denver*

15.028. Black Educational Futurism as Praxis: Re/membering Through the Curation of Black Intellectual Lineage. SIG-Critical Educators for Social Justice; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304B;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

- Blackly World Construction: Curricular Un/Makings and the Grammar of Black Joy. *Justin A. Coles, University of Massachusetts - Amherst*
- Honoring the Past, Shaping the Future: Engaging Black Preservice Math Teachers with the Black Teacher Archive. *Lateefah Ameerah Id-Deen, Kennesaw State University*
- Unforgetting and (Re)membering Black Education Theorizing in the Educational Leadership and Policy Classroom. *Darrius A. Stanley, University of Minnesota*
- Unforgetting Epistemologies: Black Feminisms, Epistemic Exclusion, and the Intellectual Labor of Black Women Scholars. *Tonisha B. Lane, Virginia Tech*

Chair: *Imani J. Wallace, University of Massachusetts - Amherst*

Discussant: *Deirdre Cobb-Roberts, University of South Florida*

15.029. Indigenous Peoples, Epistemologies And Praxis In Education. SIG-Decolonial, Postcolonial, and Anti-Colonial Studies in Education; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 301A;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

- Decolonising and Enriching the Teaching and Learning of

Mathematics through the use of Ndebele Mural Art and Indigenous Knowledge Systems. *Mogege David Mosimege, University of the Free State; Mapula Poo, University of the Free State*

Decolonizing GenAI-assisted Teaching and Learning: A Land-based Pedagogical Perspective. *Yilun Jiang, Michigan State University*

Trauma-Informed Education Through Translanguaging Practices: Culturally Sustaining Pedagogy for Indigenous Refugee Students in Brazil. *Karina O. De Paula, Texas Tech University; Michelle Angelo-Rocha, University of South Florida; Maria Janerrandra Fogaça Bispo Pereira, Universidade de Brasilia; Cátia Regina Guidio Alves de Oliveira, Brazilian National Council for Scientific and Technological Development*

Towards Anticolonial Framework for Teacher Education in Ghana. *Ali Ahmed, Texas Tech University*

Uplifting Indigenous Language Justice in Urban Schools: A Case Study of Nimalaj Be', a Maya Language Club. *Emily Grijalva, Mendez HS/LAUSD*

Discussant: *Miguel Angel Garcia-Bocanegra, Northwestern University*

15.030. Coaching Within Early Education: Lessons Learned Across Three States. SIG-Early Education and Child Development; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Georgia I;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

- Statewide Coaching in Virginia's Unified Early Childhood Education System: Initial Findings and Lessons Learned. *Ann Partee, University of Virginia; Jason Downer, University of Virginia; Amanda Paige Williford, University of Virginia*
- Reflections on Building a New State-Wide System to Support ECE Coaches: Lessons Learned. *Bridget E Hatfield, Oregon State University; Hillary R. Lewis, Oregon State University; Maya Johnson, Oregon State University; Rebekah Benkart, Oregon State University*
- Building Coaching Capacity Using A Tiered Approach: Lessons Learned in State-Wide Scale-Up. *Kathleen Artman Meeker, University of Washington; Angel Fettig, University of Washington; Carol Ann Davis, University of Washington; Scott Spaulding, University of Washington*

Chairs: *Bridget E Hatfield, Oregon State University; Ann Partee, University of Virginia*

Discussant: *Hillary R. Lewis, Oregon State University*

15.031. Examining the Role of Race and Culture in Schools and Communities. SIG-Family, School, Community Partnerships; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum B;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

White Parents' Engagement, Educational Excess, and the Pull Towards Passive Support of the Status Quo. *Jennifer L. McCarthy Foubert, North Central College*

Racialized Lived Experiences of No-Knock Raids in Canadian Policing. *Tina-Nadia Chambers, University of Guelph; Ardavan Eizadirad, Wilfrid Laurier University*

The Jeanes Supervisors of Florida: Her-Stories Of Black Women Educators' Work As A Necessary Model Of Family & Community Engagement. *Melanie M. Acosta, Florida Atlantic University*

Community-Led Pathways: Supporting Refugee Families in STEM and College Navigation. *Eugene Judson, Arizona State University; Mohammed Ibrahim, Arizona State University*

Deconstructing Eurocentric Frames: An African-Centered Analysis of Ghanaian Immigrant Family Literacies. *Sandra Boateng, Michigan State University*

Chair: *Fatima Seyma Kizil, Syracuse University*

Discussant: *Lori Delale-O'Connor, University of Pittsburgh*

15.032. Leading for Organizational Change, Resilience, and Addressing Student Behavior. SIG-Leadership for School Improvement; Paper Session

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, San Bernardino; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

All the Right Moves: Instructional Leadership and Discipline Decision-Making. *Regina Lynn Seabrook, University of Minnesota; Jeff Walls, University of Iowa*

Beyond Bouncing Back: Organizational Resilience and K-12 Leadership Adaptability During the COVID-19 Crisis. *Craig De Voto, University of Illinois at Chicago; Kate Hasler Steilen, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Shelby A. Cosner, University of Georgia; Alison Castro Superfine, University of Illinois at Chicago; Benjamin M. Superfine, University of Illinois at Chicago*

Connected Independence: The Role of Relatedness and Autonomy in Organizational Change and Organizational Learning. *Jennifer Karnopp, San Diego State University; Peter Bjorklund, University of California - San Diego*

The Ripple Effect of Explosive Student Behaviors in Elementary Schools: Recommendations for School Leaders. *Tanya DaMommio, Texas State University*

Chair: *April M. Stokes, Montclair State University*

Discussants: *Kristin Vogel-Campbell, North Point Educational Service Center; Katrina Struloeff, University of Pennsylvania*

15.033. Developments in Mathematics Teacher Preparation and Professional Development. SIG-Research in Mathematics Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum A; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Designing Effective Modeling Tasks: Lessons Learned from an Inservice Teacher Professional Development Program.

Sehrish Jabeen, Utah State University; Tye Campbell, Utah State University; Sindura Kularajan, Utah State University; Lily Roth, Utah State University

Examining Teacher Learning within Mathematics Professional Learning Communities in Relation to District Vision and Policy. *Christine Roberts, University of California - Los Angeles*

From Theory to Practice: Mathematics Methods Coursework and the Development of Culturally Relevant Mathematics Lessons. *Lara Condon, University of Memphis; Wesam M. Salem, University of Memphis*

Secondary Mathematics Teachers' Preferences and Rationales for Selecting Instructional Nudges in Online Professional Development. *Samuel Otten, University of Missouri; Olumide Banjo, University of Missouri; Zandra de Araujo, University of Florida; Amber Grace Candela, University of Missouri - St. Louis*

Discussant: *Charles E. Wilkes, University of California - Davis*

15.034. Teaching Democracy Now. SIG-Social Studies Research; Structured Poster Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 515B; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

1. The Historical and Contemporary Marginalization of Social Studies in U.S. Education: Implications for Democracy (Poster 1). *Tina Heafner, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Paul G. Fitchett, Auburn University*
2. Democratic Education and the Role of Teachers' Unions, Professional Organizations, and Working Groups (Poster 2). *Christopher C. Martell, University of Massachusetts - Boston*
3. Teaching for (and not just about) Pro-Social Political Disobedience (Poster 3). *Cathryn van Kessel, Texas Christian University; Rebeka Plots, Texas Christian University*
4. Orientations to Authority – Democracy in the Mind (Poster 4). *H. James Garrett, University of Georgia*
5. Let Us Become the Radicals They Accuse Us of Being: Social Studies Education in the Ruins of Liberal Democracy (Poster 5). *Mardi Schmeichel, University of Nebraska - Lincoln; Alexander Cuenca, Indiana University*
6. Teaching for Democracy Under Political Threats (Poster 6). *Judy L. Pace, University of San Francisco; Wayne Journell, University of North Carolina - Greensboro*
7. F*ck the Patriarchy as Democratic Action: Choosing Resistance (Poster 7). *Rebecca Cooper Geller, University of Georgia; Amelia Wheeler, Western Carolina University*
8. Keeping Queer and Trans Identities (Un)Erased (Poster 8). *J.B. Mayo, University of Minnesota*
9. Building Trust in Diverse, Credible Sources (Poster 9). *Elizabeth Reynolds, University of Maryland; Sarah McGrew,*

University of Maryland

Chairs: *Christopher H. Clark, University of North Dakota;*
Cathryn van Kessel, Texas Christian University

15.035. Cultivating Inclusive Futures: College, Career, and Community Engagement for Students with Disabilities. SIG-Special and Inclusive Education Research; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Georgia II; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

A critical analysis of work-based learning opportunities for students with intellectual disabilities in 18-21 transition programs. *Jessica K. Bacon, Montclair State University*
Life After College: Employment, Independence, and Belonging for CTP Graduates. *Hasan Aydin, Florida Gulf Coast University; Alyssa Sanabria, Florida Gulf Coast University; Bruno Halpern, Florida Gulf Coast University; Nicholas Kutz, Florida Gulf Coast University; Felicha Saintine Joseph, Florida Gulf Coast University*
Living Inclusion: Experiences in Italy from an Intentionally Inclusive Study Abroad Program. *Sara H. Petit-McClure, Syracuse University; Ethan W Jackson, Syracuse University; Christine Elaine Ashby, Syracuse University; Beth Myers, Syracuse University*

Figuring it out together: developing a mentorship program with autistic college and high school students. *Dora Dufie Onwumere, New York University; Wendy B. Martin, Education Development Center, Inc.; Wesley Alberts, New York University; Olivia Lyra Barrow, Guttman Community College; Lela Fluker, College of Staten Island; Brian Myers, New York University; Kenny Velez, College of Staten Island; Nicole Wang, New York University; Andrew Yan, New York University; Ariana Riccio Arista, Education Development Center, Inc.; Samantha Tumolo, Education Development Center, Inc.; Rita Strickland Caragliano, College of Staten Island; Louis Rotondo, College of Staten Island; Kristen Gillespie-Lynch, College of Staten Island - CUNY; Kristie Patten, New York University*

A Multiple Case Study of the College Motivation of Three Students with Intellectual Disabilities. *Masako Imanishi, University of Hawaii - Manoa*

Chair: *Ruby Batz, University of Nevada - Reno*

Division and SIG Roundtables

15.036. AERA Roundtable Session Wednesday 7:45 am; Roundtable Session

15.036-1. Reimagining the Possible: Re/Conceptualizing Leadership (Table 1). Division A - Administration; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 7:45-

9:15am

Participants:

Principal Social Justice Leadership: A Systematic Review of 20 Years of Research, 2005–2024. *Jiani Rong, East China Normal University; Shuangye Chen, East China Normal University*

Community Epistemology in Culturally Responsive School Leadership Through The Chronicle. *Priya Goel, California State University - Dominguez Hills; Theara Thun, University of Hong Kong*

Linking Distributed Leadership and Shared Leadership in K-12 Education. *ZIXIN LIU; Chun Sing Maxwell Ho, The Education University of Hong Kong; Donnie Adams, University of Malaysia*

Constructing Inclusive School Leadership: Finnish Principals' Discourses about Bridging Ideals and Practice. *Anita Hannele Jantunen, University of Helsinki; Raisa Carpelan, University of Helsinki; Anni Loukomies, University of Helsinki; Tapio Juhani Lahtero, University of Helsinki; Arto Juha Viljami Kallioniemi, University of Helsinki; Kati Sormunen, University of Helsinki*

Amplifying the Pipeline for School Administration with School Counselors. *Margarita Landeros, California State University - Dominguez Hills; Janet Garcia, California State University - Dominguez Hills*

Chair: *Jennifer Ventimiglia, Northeastern Illinois University*

15.036-2. Policy Implementation and Governance in Educational Leadership (Table 2). Division A - Administration; Roundtable Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Policy in Practice: Migrant Program Leadership Across Boundaries of Compliance, Equity, and Institutional Visibility. *Lavanya Jawaharlal, Claremont Graduate University*

Community Across Boundaries: Examining the Social Networks of State Computer Science Leaders as Drivers for Equity. *Stefanie L. Marshall, Michigan State University; Ain A. Grooms, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Joshua Childs, University of Texas at Austin; Grace L. Tukurah, Michigan State University; SJ Hemmerich, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Leading educative governance together: imagining new futures for principals and school governance. *Christine Grice, University of Sydney; Christopher W. Day, University of Nottingham; Virginia Moller, University of Sydney*

15.036-3. Leadership at Equity Intersections: Minoritized Identity, Gender, Resilience, and Advocacy (Table 3). Division A - Administration; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Collective Agency of Educational Leadership Faculty in the Restrictive Policy Climate. *Motoko Akiba, Florida State University; Daniel Moraguez, Florida State University; Mario Jackson, Florida State University; Kevin Forehand, Florida State University*

From Roots to Wings: Grounded Yet Transformative Resilience in Higher Education Leaders of Color. *Dulce Elizabeth Caldino DeNovellis, University of San Diego*

"It Makes Me Feel Less Alone": Support for LGBTQ+ Educational Leaders. *David Osworth, University of North Carolina - Greensboro; Shavonne Oliver, University of North Carolina - Greensboro*

Reclaiming Leadership Narratives: Resilience and Community Among Principals with Disabilities. *Cynthia Angélica Gallardo, Texas A&M International University; Lourdes Vilorio, Texas A&M International University; Alfredo Ramirez, Texas A&M International University*

Transformative Inquiry Pilot Study: Fostering Teacher Leadership, Advocacy & Agency. *Teresa Bruno Warkentin, University of Colorado - Boulder; Karen Crofton, University of Colorado - Boulder; Deborah K. Palmer, University of Colorado - Boulder*

Chair: *Victoria Koop, Wichita State University*

15.036-4. Leadership Preparation Access Equity: Inclusive Practices, Pathways, Technologies, and Evaluation (Table 4). Division A - Administration; Roundtable Session Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Inequitable Access to Principal Preparation: A Statewide Review of Collective Bargaining Agreements. *Maria Lewis, Pennsylvania State University; Joshua S. Almes, Brown University*

Measuring Principal Program Effectiveness: A Systematic Review of the Literature. *Rachel Roegman, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Anne Allegretti, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Paul Bruno, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Melissa Goodnight, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Haerim Lee, Chicago State University*

More Pathways, More Providers: Examining the Institutional Transformation of Administrator Preparation in California. *Rebecca Cheung, University of California - Berkeley; Melissa Itzel Virrueta-Peters, University of California - Berkeley; Michelle D. Young, University of California - Berkeley*

What Do Private Schools Look for in Principals? Evidence from Job Advertisements. *Siche Feng, Western Michigan University*

Chair: *Kimberly Jamison, University of North Carolina - Wilmington*

15.036-5. Collective (Re)membering and Imagining Futures (Table 5). Division B - Curriculum Studies; Roundtable Session Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Collective Memory As Pedagogy: A Multimodal, Historical Discourse Analysis of Vietnam War Curriculum Materials. *Minh Nghia-Nguyen, University of Massachusetts - Boston; Panayota Gounari, University of Massachusetts - Boston*

Korea as Research: Centering Indigenous Epistemologies for Futuring Curriculum Studies. *Seungho Moon, Loyola University Chicago*

Psychic Curriculum: Transindividual Processes of Educational Memory and Forgetting. *Jory Rizal, Independent Scholar*

Constructing Curriculum of Future Based on Chinese Wisdom Traditions. *Hua Zhang, Qufu Normal University*

15.036-6. Black Educational Research as Justice Praxis (Table 6). Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Opportunity Structures and the Making of a Changemaker: Black Teachers' Relational Practices as Sites of Sociopolitical Development. *LaKendrick Richardson, Auburn University*

Reimagining Retention: A Social Justice Model for Black Undergraduates in the "College-to-and-through" Movement. *Jonli Tunstall, University of California - Los Angeles; Ashley Williams, University of California - Los Angeles; Cynthia Estrada, California State University - Channel Islands; Jaylen Lowe, UCLA; Seth Duncan, University of California - Los Angeles*

Understanding Racial Harm: A Study of Discipline Disparities in Progressive Public Schools. *Gabriela López, Stanford University*

Chair: *Kaleb Germinaro, University of Illinois at Chicago*

15.036-7. Centering Student & Teacher Experiences in Educational Research (Table 7). Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Exploring Teacher Beliefs and (Mis)Behavior: A Critical Qualitative Study. *Essence Noel, California State University - Sacramento; Addison Duane, Sacramento State University*

Student-Teacher Collaborative Dialogue in a U.S. Middle School. *Laura Fittz Parks, Fort Lewis College*

"We can't have this system anymore, we have to abolish it": Social Media's Role in Shifting Youth Sociopolitical Development Admst the Dual Pandemics. *Angela L.*

Malorni, Rutgers University; Sara Wilf, California Polytechnic State University

Chair: *Laura Fittz Parks, Fort Lewis College*

15.036-8. Imagining and Planning for Innovation: System Change in Out-of-School Time (Table 8). SIG-Out-of-School Time; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Enhancing SEL in OST Programs: Implementation Lessons from Washington's Boys & Girls Clubs. *Helen Lee, foundry10; Janelle Salcedo, foundry10; Jovani Azpeitia, foundry10*

Exploring Implementation Deviations in China's Out-of-School Time (OST) Reform: A Smith Model Perspective. *Yan Chunshun, East China Normal University; Shiqi Teng, Jishou University; Mengting Qian, East China Normal University; Tianyi Sun, East China Normal University*

Exploring Organizational Climate in 4-H Youth Development from 2017 to 2025. *Evelyn Mandujano, University of California - Davis; Steven M. Worker, University of California Agriculture and Natural Resources; Kali Trzesniewski, University of California - Davis*

The Finnish Model for Leisure Activities: Youth Voice Reimagined. *Risto Marttinen, George Mason University*
Unspoken Challenges to Data Collection and Use in OST Programs. *Arielle Lentz, University of Delaware; Megan E. Howe, University of Rhode Island; Virginia Killian Lund, University of Rhode Island*

15.036-9. Care, Motherhood, and Identity Work in AANHPI Communities (Table 9). SIG-Asian Americans and Pacific Islanders in Education and Research; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Cultural Bridges that Connecting Futures: Asian Immigrants' Cultural Identity Integration through Transformative Learning Theory. *Yilu Guo, Teachers College, Columbia University*

From Caregiver to Community Leader: Asian American Parents' Journey in Disability Activism. *Jenny Yang, St. John's University*

Neither Here nor There: Mother-Scholars' Perspectives on 1.5 Generation Asian American. *Shuling Yang, University of Maryland - Baltimore County; Elizabeth Isidro, Western Michigan University*

Chair: *Nicole Marie DelMastro-Jeffery, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

15.037. AERA Roundtable Session Wednesday 7:45 am - Gold 1; Roundtable Session

15.037-1. Tracing Trajectories: Teachers Reframing Transnational Identities and Practice (Table 1). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Examining Critical Cosmopolitan Moments in Digitally Mediated Transnational Interactions between Chinese and American Language Teachers. *Yuxiang Zhu, Minnesota State University - Mankato*

Navigating Pedagogical Orientations: A Case Study of a Twice Trained Teacher. *Ian Parker Renga, University of Southern Maine*

Reframing Identity Through Hallyu: A Collaborative Autoethnography of Korean Teacher Educators. *SungEun Min, Kutztown University of Pennsylvania; Gayoung Choi, University of Nebraska - Lincoln*

Rest-Less Teachers in Testing Conditions: A Comparative Case Study of Primary School Teachers in Karnataka, India. *Amogh Basavaraj, Florida State University*

To transcend the 'humanistic versus neoliberal' narratives? Preservice teachers' profiling of globally competent teachers and visions of their 'possible professional self'. *Ji Ying, Education University of Hong Kong*

Chair: *Yuxiang Zhu, Minnesota State University - Mankato*

15.037-2. Opening Doors or Shifting Barriers? Policy Implementation and Futures of Educational Access (Table 2). Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Access Reimagined: Disability, Opportunity, and Outcomes for Students with Disabilities under a Graduation Pathway Reform. *Elizabeth Huffaker, University of Florida; Katharine Parham Malhotra, University of Virginia*

Navigating Educational Change: The Role of School District Leadership in Implementing Ontario's Grade 9 De-streamed Mathematics Curriculum Policy. *Zian Zhang, University of Toronto - OISE; Douglas E. McDougall, University of Toronto - OISE*

Reimagining Education Policy in Ghana: Uncovering Deficit Discourses and Political Spectacle in the Free Senior High School Policy. *Mohammed Ibrahim, Arizona State University*

Shaping Futures: The Association between Guaranteed College Admission Policies and Students' Educational Trajectories. *Seungbae Kim, Florida State University*

15.037-3. Evolving Pedagogies in a Digital and Global Age (Table 3). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Teaching in Diverse Schools, Learning Globally: Developing Teachers of Color through International Exchange and Reflection. *Kevin M. Wong, Pepperdine University; Anthony Collatos, Pepperdine University*

The Impact of Digital Literacy on Teachers' Well-Being: The Mediating Role of Teaching Collaboration and Self-Efficacy. *Qiran Wang, Zhejiang International Studies University; Hang Xu, Zhejiang International Studies University; Tingyan Wu, Zhejiang International Studies University*

The relationship between teachers' openness, creative beliefs, self-efficacy, ICT competencies and creative pedagogy. *Wen SHAO, University of Hong Kong; Xianhan Huang, The Education University of Hong Kong; Shiyu Zhang, University of Hong Kong*

Chair: *Charity M. Dacey, Touro University*

15.037-4. Critical Examination of Race, Ethnicity, Class, and Gender Roundtable: Asian American Experiences, Resistance, and Justice (Table 4). SIG-Critical

Examination of Race, Ethnicity, Class and Gender in Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Counter-stories of Asian American Childhood: Standing Up for One Another At School & Online. *Yoonjin Nam-Huh, California State University - Dominguez Hills*

Unmasking the Model Minority Myth: Intergenerational AAPI Voices for Equity, Advocacy, and Future Research. *Nirmla Griarte Flores, California State Polytechnic University - Pomona; Kimmie Tang, Alder Graduate School of Education*

How South Asian American Women's Experiences With Parental Academic Expectations Reinforce Seeking Out External Validation. *Zora Haque, Harvard University*

Reclaiming Liminality: Korean American Adoptee and School Leadership. *Jia Liang, Kansas State University*

Reclaiming Yet Ongoing: A Two Part Phenomenological Study of Chinese Queer Diaspora in the U.S. through a Queer Literacy Workshop Series. *Yih Ren, University of San Francisco*

Chair: *Eujin Park, Stanford University*

15.037-5. Toward an Abolitionist Leadership Theory:

Concepts and Cases of Anti-Racist Educational

Leadership (Table 5). SIG-Critical Examination of Race, Ethnicity, Class and Gender in Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Black Males as "Folk Devils": Examining Moral Panics in K-12 Education. *Cleo Wadley, Harris County Department of Education*

The Role of the Principal in Transgressing the Social Construction of Race in Schools. *Cornell Thomas, Texas Christian University*

Overt and Covert Anti-Racist Pedagogies: Student Memories from Secondary and Postsecondary Schooling. *Marcus Johnson, Virginia Tech*

Educational Leadership at the Intersection of Race and Poverty in American Schools: Countering Racial Inequality. *Patrick M. Jenlink, Stephen F. Austin State University*

Preparing Anti-Racist/Abolitionist Educational Leaders for Transformative Praxis. *Chetanath Gautam, Delaware State University*

Anti-Racism and Ed Leadership: Reimagining Educational Practice for Equity and Justice. *Anthony Walker, Tarrant County College*

Chairs: *Rhonda Humphries, The New Teacher Project; Charles L. Lowery, Virginia Tech*

15.038. AERA Roundtable Session Wednesday 7:45 am - Gold 2; Roundtable Session

15.038-1. Implementing Interventions in Social Emotional Learning (Table 1). SIG-Social and Emotional Learning;

Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Benefits of Second Step® to Classroom Social Climates Following Two Years of Implementation. *Kimberly R. M. Osborne, Arizona State University; Sabina Low, Arizona State University; Keith Smolkowski, Oregon Research Institute*

Exploratory Case Study of Middle School Teachers' Implementation Fidelity of Social-Emotional Learning Curriculum. *Laura Rizo, Rizo Speaks Life; Leslie K. Curda, National University*

FriendZi's: Piloting a Game-Based SEL Curriculum for Elementary Student Engagement and Emotional Development. *Manisha Naresh Nagpal, Duquesne University; Sophia Shieh, Duquesne University; Michael Maryniak, Duquesne University; Anthony Carbone, Independent Researcher; Kara Carola, Independent Researcher*

Meet Up Buddy Up Intervention Effects on Peer Aggression and Victimization. *Ashley R. McDonald, Arizona State University; Haining Ren, Arizona State University; Laura Hanish, Arizona State University; Carol Lynn Martin, Arizona State University; Sabina Low, Arizona State University; Richard A. Fabes, Arizona State University; Cindy Miller, Texas State University; Lorey A. Wheeler, University of Nebraska - Lincoln*

Promoting Conflict Resolution Skills through an Art-Based Social and Emotional Learning (ABSEL) Curriculum.

Mousumi De, University of Redlands

Chair: *Sara E. Rimm-Kaufman, University of Virginia*

15.038-2. Community as a Transformative Site of Sharing Literacies, Knowledge, and Stories (Table 2). SIG-Writing and Literacies; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Community Writing Circles as a Site for Intergenerational Queer Knowledge-Sharing. *Jimmy McLean, University of Texas at Austin*

Powerful Pens: Black Girls' Literacies and Stories in Boston. *Ashley Houston-King, Boston University*

Restoring Literate Identity: Multimodal Inquiry and Transformation in a Community-Based Literacy Partnership. *Maggie Bryant, Baylor University*

Chair: *Clara Abbott, University of Pennsylvania*

15.038-3. Conjuring Criticality and Community Through Youth's Multimodal Literacies (Table 3). SIG-Writing and Literacies; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Beyond Silence: Cultivating Literacy and Writing Among Immigrant and Refugee Youth Through Trauma-Informed Arts-Based Practices. *Angela M. Wiseman, North Carolina State University; Haleema Khalil, North Carolina State University; Majid Komasi, North Carolina State University*

Queer all along: (Re)imagining theories of critical multimodal composition through queer theoretical lenses. *Kris Bell, Claremont Graduate University*

Chair: *Layla Coleman, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

15.038-4. Computational Thinking Assessment and Learning Across K-12 (Table 4). Division C - Learning and Instruction; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Centering Test Fairness in Early Childhood Computational Thinking Assessment Practices: A Regularized MNLFA approach. *Chungsoo Na, Utah State University; Lingna Xu, Utah State University; Jody E. Clarke-Midura, Utah State University; Willa van Dijk, Utah State University*

Storytelling in ScratchJr: Integrating Computational Thinking and Writing in Early Childhood Classrooms. *Jiyoung Kim, California State Polytechnic University - Pomona; Daniel J. Castner, Indiana University; Curtis J. Bonk, Indiana University*

Pre-Service Teachers' Perceptions of Integrated Computational

Thinking-STEM Education and Insights Comparisons with In-Service Teachers. *Linwei Yu, The University of Hong Kong*

Exploring Student Experiences in a CS-Integrated Science Curriculum: A Project-Based Ocean Exploration with Robotics. *Xin Xia, University of Georgia; Jennifer L. Chiu, University of Virginia; Kim Wilkens, University of Virginia*
Subgroup and Longitudinal Measurement Invariance of the Computational Thinking Test - Short (CTt-S). *Joseph C. Tise, Institute for Advancing Computing Education; Monica McGill, Institute for Advancing Computing Education*

Chair: *Youn Seon Lim, University of Cincinnati*

15.038-5. Learning in Community: New Perspectives on Agency and Change (Table 5). SIG-Cultural-Historical Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Collective Transformative Agency: Advancing the Voice of Ordinary People to Drive Educational Decision Making. *Elizabeth Schrader, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Dian Mawene, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Developing a Praxis of Solidarity - Community Collective Actions through Expansive Learning. *Sophina Choudry, University of Manchester*

Recapitulation as Developmental Mediation of Temporal Structure. *Adam LeRoy, HighScope Educational Research Foundation*

Third Spaces as Relationally-Mediated and Historicized Learning. *Ava Jackson, Loyola University Chicago; Paige A Hicks, Loyola University Chicago; Corey A Winchester, Northwestern University*

Chair: *Ivana Guarrasi, Minnesota State University - Mankato*
Discussant: *Lara M. Beaty, LaGuardia Community College - CUNY*

15.038-6. Decisions, Costs, and Weekly Dynamics: New Angles on Situated Expectancy-Value Theory (Table 6). SIG-Motivation in Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Differentiation of Math Motivation in Upper Elementary Grades: The Emerging Role of Perceived Cost. *Jimin Suh, Korea University - Brain and Motivation Research Institute; Seohee Park, Korea University - Brain and Motivation Research Institute; Jihyun Lee, Korea University - Brain and Motivation Research Institute; Allan L. Wigfield, University of Maryland; Mimi Bong, Korea University*

Good Enough to Persist? Decision-Making Tendencies and Motivation in Early STEM Coursework. *Syntia Hadis; Emily Quinn Rosenzweig, Teachers College, Columbia University; Patrick N. Beymer, University of Cincinnati*

Mapping the Weekly Dynamics of Expectancy-Value-Cost Beliefs: Subject-Specific Patterns in Motivational Networks. *Xinyi Shi, McGill University; Yi Jiang, East China Normal University*

Perceived Cost Among Underrepresented College Students: Challenges, Assets, and Support Resources. *Jennifer Henderlong Corpus, Reed College; Jayna Mumo, Reed College*

Chair: *Delaram A. Totonchi, University of Virginia*

15.038-7. Arts based educational reesarch and critical narrative(s) (Table 7). SIG-Arts-Based Educational Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Listening-for Living Voices: Archival Songs as Historical Inquiry in Dialogue with an Oral History Archive. *Laura Montanari, Montclair State University*

“I love my morenita skin.” Creating a Culturally Empowering and Unapologetic Social Justice-Oriented Children’s Book. *Martin Alberto Gonzalez, Portland State University*

Rave as Method: Community Engagement, Knowledge Co-production, and Creative Disruption in Academic Writing. *Alexander Fedorov, University of Hong Kong; Euan Auld, The Education University of Hong Kong*

Chair: *Ashley D. Domínguez, University of Arizona*

Discussant: *Patience Amadu, University of Colorado - Colorado Springs*

15.039. AERA Roundtable Session Wednesday 7:45 am - Gold 3; Roundtable Session

15.039-1. Re/membering Beyond the Settler Colonial Academy: Methods Rooted in and for Ancestral Knowledges (Table 1). Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Re/membering our Desires in Research: Methods for writing and researching the future. *Cydney Y. Caradonna, University of Utah*

Methods of Central American Epistemic Sovereignty. *Eileen M. Galvez, Colorado State University*

Expanding Affirming Methodologies as a Diasporic-Affirming Methodology in the U.S. Academy. *Luz Nereida Burgos-Lopez, University of Connecticut*

Chair: *Eileen M. Galvez, Colorado State University*

Discussant: *Omi Salas-SantaCruz, University of Utah*

15.039-2. Beyond the Numbers: Advancing Mixed Methods through Critical Race Theory, Quantitative

Ethnography, and Network Analysis for Educational Justice (Table 2). Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Unsettling Norms and Building Futures: Critical Quantitative Ethnography for Equity and Epistemic Justice. *Adaurennaya C. Onyewuenyi, The College of New Jersey; Nichole M. Garcia, Rutgers University; David W. Shaffer, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Unveiling the Types of Knowledge Brokers and their Behavioral Patterns in Informal Social Networks. *Martin Rehm, University of Southern Denmark; Elisabeth Munth Andersen, University of Southern Denmark; Anita Caduff, University of Michigan; Mimi Lockton, University of California - San Diego; Alan J. Daly, University of California - San Diego*

Chair: *Darane Taychachaiwongse Teng, University of Colorado - Denver*

15.039-3. Designing and Evolving Programs for Continuous Educational Improvement (Table 3). Division H - Research, Evaluation and Assessment in Schools; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Evaluating Communities of Practice that Aim to Build Educational Leaders’ Capacity for Equity-Centered Continuous Improvement. *Lizzet Rojas, University of California - Los Angeles*

From Education Evaluation Research to Evidence-Based Impact: Continuous Program Improvement in the Senior Odyssey Summer Program. *Gema Cardona, Berkeley University of California; Saadeddin Bozkurt, University of California - Santa Cruz; Shelly Horn, University of California - Santa Cruz*

Program Evaluation: Pilot Algebra-for-Engineering Elective Class for Secondary Students in Mid-Atlantic Urban Public School District. *Alexis Daniels, Johns Hopkins University; Joseph M. Reilly, Johns Hopkins University*

Scaling Up Summer Learning: The Impacts of Summer Boost Across Seven Cities. *Geoffrey D. Borman, Arizona State University; Jaymes Pyne, Stanford University; Jeremy Pyne, Pyne Research Associates; Erin McGoldrick, MGT of America, Inc.; Caitlin Day-Lewis, MGT.US; Jessica Rosner, MGT of America, Inc.; Tanya Pramatarova, MGT of America, Inc.; Leah Weissburg, MGT of America, Inc.; Alex Sanchez, MGT of America, Inc.; Keanu McDonough, MGT of America, Inc.; Alicia Yang, MGT of America, Inc.; Julia Horwitz, MGT of America, Inc.; Lawand Yaseen, MGT of America, Inc.; McKain Williams, MGT of America, Inc.; Grace Thompson, MGT of America, Inc.; Erica Wilson,*

MGT of America, Inc.

Understanding Implementation of Tiered Intervention Platforms and Enabling School-Wide Conditions for Accelerating Student Growth. *Katherine McKee, Vanderbilt University; Changhee Lee, Vanderbilt University; Krista Davis, Metro Nashville Public Schools; Kathryn Pattullo, Metro Nashville Public Schools; Melissa Brock, Metro Nashville Public Schools; Marcia Barnes, Vanderbilt University*

Chair: *Xueying Gao, University at Albany - SUNY*

15.039-4. Measuring Success: Readiness, Performance and Proficiency (Table 4). Division I - Education in the Professions; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Assessment of Pediatric Residents in the United States by Sex, Ethnoracial and Intersectional Group. *Hannah L. Kakara Anderson, Maastricht University; Daniel C West, University of Pennsylvania; Alan Schwartz, University of Illinois at Chicago; Laura Lockwood, University of Colorado Anschutz Medical Campus; Caroline Rassbach, Stanford University School of Medicine; Ariel Winn, Boston Children's Hospital; Catherine Michaelson, Northwestern Feinberg School of Medicine; Benjamin Kinnear, University of Cincinnati College of Medicine; Jerome G Chen, Orlando Health; Abigail Martini, Alabama College of Osteopathic Medicine; David Turner, American Board of Pediatrics; Daniel S Schumacher, University of Cincinnati*

English Language Proficiency in Healthcare Professions:

Minimum Passing Scores for Foreign Health Care Workers. *Carina McCormick, TruMerit (formerly CGFNS)*

Impact of Peer-Facilitated Preparatory Program Towards Medical Students' Readiness and Performance in National Licensing Examination. *Prattama Santoso Utomo, University of Rochester; Jialin Yan, University of Rochester*

Profiling Student Self-Assessment Engagement in Engineering Education: A Cluster-Based Approach. *Vincent OLUWASETO Fakiyesi, University of Georgia; Taiwo Feyijimi, University of Georgia; Nathaniel Hunsu, University of Georgia*

Chair: *Kelly Edwards, American Board of Pediatrics*

15.039-5. The Power of Collaborative Research: Co-Constructing Inquiries, Worlds, and Realities (Table 5). SIG-Qualitative Research; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Using Game Aesthetics to Explore the Affective Atmosphere of School Buildings. *Elizabeth De Freitas, Adelphi University; Matthew X. Curinga, Adelphi University*

Collegial Ethnographic Research: Transforming Social Practices Through Koryosaram Youth and College Student

Collaboration. *Ahram Park, University of Utah*
Confluences and Challenges for Emerging Scholars in Critical and Indigenous Methodologies and Case Study Methodology. *Cheetara A Hudson, Loyola University Chicago; Eleanor Charlton, Loyola University Chicago; Erika E de la Riva, Loyola University Chicago; Kristlyn Thomas, Loyola University Chicago; Leanne Kallemeyn, Loyola University Chicago*

Reality Pedagogy and/as Cosmopolitan Praxis: Student-Driven Instruction in the Age of Polarization. *Christopher Emdin, Teachers College, Columbia University; Qiana Spellman, St. John's University*

Chair: *Malayna Bernstein, University of Toronto*

Discussant: *LeAnne C. Salazar Montoya, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*

15.039-6. Reflective Practices in the Context of Teaching Research Methods and Statistics (Table 6). SIG-Teaching and Learning Research Methods; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Tracking Relational Dynamics in Mathematics Teacher Collaborative Decision-Making: A Dialogue Mapping Approach. *Qiuyu Chen, University of Michigan; Amanda Marie Milewski, University of Michigan*

Making Research Methods Training Real: Practice Reflections on Incorporating a Whole-Class Research Project. *Rachelle Kist Hackett, University of the Pacific; Jacquelyn Nott, University of the Pacific; Carrie Rohrbach, University of the Pacific; Adriana Brogger, University of the Pacific*
Teaching Graduate Statistics I: Modernizing for a New Generation of Learners. *Lori A. Foote, University of Cincinnati*

Chair: *Maria D. Vásquez-Colina, Florida Atlantic University*

Division and SIG Posters

15.040. AERA Poster Session Wednesday 7:45am; Poster Session

15.040-1. Using Education, Place, Space, and Time in the Pursuit of Educational Justice and Renewal. Division G - Social Context of Education; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 7:45-9:15am

Posters:

1. Amplifying Belonging: A Critical Amplification Methodology of Media Discourses on Girls in Education, Migration, and STEM (Poster 1). *Aaminah Norris, California State University - Sacramento; Maha Elsinbawi, California State University - Sacramento; Leena A. Jackson, California State University - Sacramento*

2. "And Now it's Just, Like, Crap.": Considering Youth Wellbeing Through Aesthetic Encounters in Sites of Learning and Leisure (Poster 2). *Christine Balt, University of Toronto Schools*
3. "An Upstanding Citizen of Our City": Analysis of Websites of Public Schools Named After Confederates (Poster 3). *Cheyenne Phillips, Southern Methodist University; Meredith Paige Richards, Southern Methodist University*
4. Displaced Imagination: Palestinian Children's Visions for Their Desired Educational Futures (Poster 4). *Souhaila Nassar, Boston University*
5. Exploring Cross-cultural Predictors of Creativity as a Value-added Construct: Comparative Multi-level Analysis Using PISA Data (Poster 5). *Kylee Healy, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Jaekyung Lee, University at Buffalo - SUNY*
6. Key Insights on Education for Planetary Futures (Poster 6). *Iveta Silova, Arizona State University; Andrea E. Weinberg, Arizona State University; Michelle Jordan, Arizona State University; Victoria Desimoni, Arizona State University; Dilraba Anayatova, Arizona State University; Carrie Karsgaard, Cape Breton University*
7. Navigating Early Childhood Education in Crisis: The Power of Parenting Apps to Enhance Parent Self-Efficacy (Poster 7). *Luisa Prokupek, University of Bamberg; Theresia Gabriele Hummel, University of Bamberg; Sabine Blaurock, University of Bamberg; Franziska Cohen, University of Freiburg; Yvonne Anders, University of Bamberg*
8. Ni nos incluyen: Emerging Multilingual Learners Perceptions of Exclusion (Poster 8). *Marcela Alvarez, University of California - Santa Barbara; Jin-Sook Lee, University of California - Santa Barbara*
9. Using Cognitive Interviewing to Conceptualize a Measure of Teacher Critical Consciousness (Poster 9). *Aberjohm Espinoza, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Aixa D. Marchand, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*
10. Mapping Escape: Articulations of Agency Within Educational Enclosure (Poster 10). *Anisa Yudawanti, Stanford University*
11. Constructing Cultural Memory: A Spatial and Narrative Analysis of a Chinese Education Museum (Poster 11). *Xiaoben Liu, Fujian Normal University; Yue Sun, Shanghai University of Sport*

15.040-2. Digital Belonging and Literacy. Division G - Social Context of Education; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 7:45-9:15am

Poster:

12. Digital Belonging and Future Imaginaries: Heritage Exploration in Asian Diasporic Youths' Use of Social Media (Poster 12). *Zixin Chen, University of Washington; Anqi Zu, University of Washington*

15.040-3. Division H: Graduate Student Research Grant

Awardees. Division H - Research, Evaluation and Assessment in Schools; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 7:45-9:15am

Posters:

13. Constraining Creativity: Analyzing [the] PISA Creative Thinking Assessment (Poster 13). *Yuyang Shen, University of North Texas*
14. Developing and Validating a Performance-Based Assessment of Systems Thinking in Elementary Science Classrooms (Poster 14). *Yameng Cui, Lehigh University*
15. The Pendulum Swings Back: Test or No Test? Admission Decision-Makers' Perspectives on the Effectiveness of Test-Optional Policies (Poster 15). *Kiya Ma, University of Kansas*

15.040-4. Lives of Teachers SIG Poster Session. SIG-Lives of Teachers; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 7:45-9:15am

Posters:

16. Exploring the Relationship Among Teachers' Interpersonal Emotion Regulation, Faculty Trust, and Work Engagement (Poster 16). *Wenyan Jiang, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Hongbiao Yin, The Chinese University of Hong Kong*
17. Filipino Teachers' Call to Teach as a Dynamic Sequence of Gift-giving (Poster 17). *Eunice Tan Contreras, The Education University of Hong Kong*
18. Investigating Waldorf Education through Teachers' Perspectives: A Case Study (Poster 18). *Isabella Daniels, Reed College; Pauline Ho, Reed College*
19. Preparing Preservice Teachers to Meet Culturally and Linguistically Diverse Students' Needs Through Culturally Sustaining Pedagogy (Poster 20). *Tala M. Karkar Esperat, Eastern New Mexico University; Tsitsi Nyabando, Eastern New Mexico University*
20. The Forgotten Voice in Teacher Preparation: Transforming Teacher Residencies Alongside the Community (Poster 21). *Robert Lee, National University; Nilsa J. Thorsos, National University; Dina Pacis, National University San Diego*
21. Tracking the trajectory: Changes in teacher self-efficacy during the first three years of teaching in urban Catholic Schools (Poster 22). *Myra Rosen-Reynoso, Boston College; Audrey A. Friedman, Boston College; Charles T Cownie, Boston College*
22. Decision-Making Processes of Revealing Identities for Teachers with Concealable Stigmatized Identities (Poster 23). *Yijia Chen, University of Arizona; Dionne Cross Francis, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Ji Y. Hong, University of Arizona; Travis Jon Dean, University of Arizona; Soojeong Lee, University of Arizona; Lijie Liu, University of Arizona; Taylor A. Roloff, University of Arizona; Jing Zhao, Educational Psychology; Paul A Schutz, University of Arizona*
23. Retention Through Redesign: How Flexible Scheduling

Supports Special Education Teachers (Poster 24). *Cyndi Riggs, Hurst-Euleless-Bedford Independent School District; Lauren E. Allen, Hurst-Euleless-Bedford Independent School District; Rene Riek, Hurst-Euleless-Bedford Independent School District*

15.040-5. Insights from Large-Scale Assessments: Advancing Methods, Measurement, and Learning Opportunities.

SIG-Large-Scale Assessment; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 7:45-9:15am

Posters:

24. Academic Transitions: Analyzing STAAR Performance of Emergent Bilingual Students from 4th to 6th Grade (Poster 25). *Russen R Vela, South Middle School; Lori Kupczynski, Texas A&M University - Kingsville; Kelly S. Hall, Texas A&M University - Kingsville; Daniella G. Varela, Texas A&M University - Kingsville*
25. Analyzing PIRLS 2021 Türkiye Data Using Cognitive Diagnostic Modeling (Poster 26). *Sedat Sen, Harran University; Nihal Burcin Bircan, Turkish National Ministry of Education*
26. Centralized Curricula Content Coverage and Student Achievement in Mathematics and Science Education: Evidence from TIMSS (Poster 27). *Marlen Holtmann, IEA Data Processing and Research Center; Alec Kennedy, IEA Hamburg; Rolf Strietholt, IEA Hamburg*
27. Home Learning Environments Bolster Students' Academic Resilience during the COVID-19 Pandemic: Evidence from PIRLS (Poster 28). *Yufang Ruan, Zhejiang University; Alec Kennedy, IEA Hamburg; Rolf Strietholt, IEA Hamburg*
28. Overrepresentation of Female Teachers in Secondary Education and Gender Achievement Gaps in PISA 2022 (Poster 29). *Hans Luyten, Universiteit Twente*

15.040-6. Teaching with and through AI: Reimagining Classroom Practice.

SIG-Technology as an Agent of Change in Teaching and Learning; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 7:45-9:15am

Posters:

29. Transforming EFL Learning: The Promise and Challenges of Generative AI Integration in Higher Education (Poster 30). *Siyuan Chen, College of William & Mary*
30. Triadic Collaborative Intelligence in High School Algebra: A Case Study of Student–Teacher–AI Interaction (Poster 31). *Zilong Pan, Lehigh University; Zilu Jiang, Johns Hopkins University; Shen Ba, The Education University of Hong Kong; Chenglu Li, University of Utah*
31. AI as Reflective Partner: Analyzing Pre-Service Teachers' Growth in ELL Instruction (Poster 32). *Donna Wake, University of Central Arkansas; Nykela Jackson, University of Central Arkansas; Lisa Mack, University of Central Arkansas*

32. Co-Designing Lessons with AI: Elementary Teachers' Use of Generative AI for Student-Centered Learning (Poster 33). *Seoyeon Choi, Korea University; Seulgi Jeong, Korea University; Yeongje Kim, Korea University; Insook Han, Korea University*

33. Generative AI as Pedagogical Partner: Adoption, Challenges, and Transformation in U.S. Language Classrooms (Poster 34). *Jue Wang, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Kristin Davin, University of North Carolina - Charlotte*

34. Investigating Student Engagement and Ethical Reflection through Generative AI in Graduate Instructional Design (Poster 35). *Scott H. Moss, National University; Dwayne Wood, National University*

35. Moving Beyond Efficiency: How Teacher Educators Reconsidered Their Beliefs and Practices with Generative AI (Poster 36). *Luqing Zang, Slippery Rock University of Pennsylvania; Jingwen He, University of North Texas; Yesim Nur Akar Hozman, Michigan State University*

15.040-7. Giftedness, Creativity, and Talent Poster Sessions.

SIG-Research on Giftedness, Creativity and Talent; Poster Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 7:45-9:15am

Posters:

36. Creativity Assessment and Machine Creativity Using Generative AI in a Sandbox Physics Game (Poster 37). *Seyedahmad Rahimi, University of Florida; Salah Esmaeilgoujar, University of Florida; Hongming Li, University of Florida*
37. Is Past Achievement Equitably Predictive of High Achievers' Future Achievement? Examining Moderation Effects of Race/Ethnicity (Poster 38). *Elizabeth Scallan, Texas A&M University; Maryann R. Hebda; Micayla Gooden, Texas A&M University; Nipah Onkananuwonk, Texas A&M University; Karen E. Rambo-Hernandez, Texas A&M University*
38. The Impact of Test Preparation on Cognitive Abilities Testing with Diverse Student Populations (Poster 39). *Debi K. Torres, Baylor University; Fatih Ozkan, Baylor University; Aysil Agaya, Baylor University*
39. Designing Holistic Talent Development Programs: A Critical Study from Framework to Implementation (Poster 40). *Veena Kulkarni, Jnana Prabodhini, India; Aparnagouri Phatak, Jnana Prabodhini's Institute of Psychology; Kshama Datar, ExtraHop; Aakash Arvind Chowkase, Yale University*
40. Profiles of Gifted Adolescents in Gifted Science Schools: Academic Self-Concept and STEM Career Aspirations (Poster 41). *Seon-Young Lee, Seoul National University; Jungmin Woo; Donggun An, Incheon National University; Sun Young Hwang, Seoul National University*

15.040-8. Emerging Topics in Second Language Research. SIG-

Second Language Research; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall -
Exhibit Hall A; 7:45-9:15am

Posters:

41. A Longitudinal Investigation of Achievement Emotions and Engagement in Chinese EFL SPOC-Based Blended Learning (Poster 42). *banban Li, University of Science and Technology Beijing; Miroslaw Pawlak, Adam Mickiewicz University*
42. A Two-Stage SEM-ANN Approach to Predict L2 Learner Satisfaction in Chinese MOOCs: The Role of Community Presence (Poster 43). *Yun Li, Sichuan University; Jining Han, Southwest University; Yuying Yang, Southwest University; Kunran Duan, Tianfu College of SWUFE*
43. Shaping Young Minds: The Role of Growth Mindset in K-12 Language Learning Success. (Poster 44). *Ran Gao, University of Florida; Congzhi Ma, University of Florida; Loraine Cisternas-Garcia, University of Florida*
44. The Impact of Comprehension-Focused Digital Reading on National Literacy Outcomes: Evidence from Seychelles (Poster 45). *Carol M Johnson, Renaissance Learning Inc. - Wisconsin Rapids, WI; Chris McKenzie, Renaissance Learning*
45. Struggling Toward Development: Understanding Second Language Learning Through a Vygotskian Lens (Poster 46). *Zhaoyu Wang-Doyle, University of Massachusetts - Amherst*

15.040-9. Advancing Learning, Engagement, and Support.

SIG-Special and Inclusive Education Research; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall -
Exhibit Hall A; 7:45-9:15am

Posters:

46. Assessment of Creative Potential in Children and Adolescents with Typical Development, Giftedness, and Twice-Exceptionality (Poster 47). *Tatiana De Cassia Nakano, Pontifical University Catholic of Campinas; João Vitor Sarôa Brandine, Pontifical Catholic University of Campinas; Mariana Dal Póz, Pontifical Catholic University of Campinas; Paloma do Nascimento Vilvert, Pontifical Catholic University of Campinas; Maria Eduarda Vieira de Andrade, Pontifical Catholic University of Campinas; Anna Luisa Penteado Garcia, Pontifical Catholic University of Campinas*
47. Challenges and Sustainability of Autism Support Programs in U.S. Higher Education: Perspectives from Program Directors (Poster 48). *Han Wang, University of South Carolina; Jiaojiao Zhu, University of South Carolina*
48. Environmental Indicators of Engagement Tool: Development, Preliminary Technical Adequacy, and Initial Field Experiences (Poster 49). *Jeong Hoon Choi, University of Kansas; Allyson Satter, University of Kansas; Sheila Wells-Moreaux, University of Kansas; Karmen Clark, University of Kansas*

49. Advancing Future Social Capabilities: Exploring Theory of Mind Training for Autism Spectrum Disorder — a Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis (Poster 50). *Huan Huang, East China Normal University; Sheng Xu, East China Normal University*
50. Cognitive and Language Profiles of Arabian Individuals with Reading Difficulties: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis (Poster 51). *Meshal Alafeasi, University of Texas at Austin; Peng Peng, University of Texas at Austin*

15.041. e-Lightning Ed-Talk Session 1 - Stage 1.

AERA e-Lightning Ed-Talks; AERA Ed Talk
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Exhibit Hall A -
Stage 1; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

- Ni nos incluyen: Emerging Multilingual Learners Perceptions of Exclusion (Stage 1, 7:50 AM). *Marcela Alvarez, University of California - Santa Barbara; Jin-Sook Lee, University of California - Santa Barbara*
- Key Insights on Education for Planetary Futures (Stage 1, 7:59 AM). *Iveta Silova, Arizona State University; Andrea E. Weinberg, Arizona State University; Michelle Jordan, Arizona State University; Victoria Desimoni, Arizona State University; Dilraba Anayatova, Arizona State University; Carrie Karsgaard, Cape Breton University*
- Exploring Cross-cultural Predictors of Creativity as a Value-added Construct: Comparative Multi-level Analysis Using PISA Data (Stage 1, 8:08 AM). *Kylee Healy, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Jaekyung Lee, University at Buffalo - SUNY*
- Displaced Imagination: Palestinian Children's Visions for Their Desired Educational Futures (Stage 1, 8:17 AM). *Souhaila Nassar, Boston University*
- "And Now it's Just, Like, Crap.:" Considering Youth Wellbeing Through Aesthetic Encounters in Sites of Learning and Leisure (Stage 1, 8:26 AM). *Christine Balt, University of Toronto Schools*
- Digital Belonging and Future Imaginaries: Heritage Exploration in Asian Diasporic Youths' Use of Social Media (Stage 1, 8:35 AM). *Zixin Chen, University of Washington; Anqi Zu, University of Washington*
- Overrepresentation of Female Teachers in Secondary Education and Gender Achievement Gaps in PISA 2022 (Stage 1, 8:44 AM). *Hans Luyten, Universiteit Twente*
- Chair: *Steven M. Sanders, Oregon State University*

15.042. e-Lightning Ed-Talk Session 1 - Stage 2.

AERA e-Lightning Ed-Talks; AERA Ed Talk
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Exhibit Hall A -
Stage 2; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

- The Forgotten Voice in Teacher Preparation: Transforming Teacher Residencies Alongside the Community (Stage 2, 7:50 AM). *Robert Lee, National University; Nilisa J. Thorsos, National University; Dina Pacis, National*

University San Diego

Decision-Making Processes of Revealing Identities for Teachers with Concealable Stigmatized Identities (Stage 2, 7:59 AM). *Yijia Chen, University of Arizona; Dionne Cross Francis, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Ji Y. Hong, University of Arizona; Travis Jon Dean, University of Arizona; Soojeong Lee, University of Arizona; Lijie Liu, University of Arizona; Taylor A. Roloff, University of Arizona; Jing Zhao, Educational Psychology; Paul A Schutz, University of Arizona*

Filipino Teachers' Call to Teach as a Dynamic Sequence of Gift-giving (Stage 2, 8:08 AM). *Eunice Tan Contreras, The Education University of Hong Kong*

Creativity Assessment and Machine Creativity Using Generative AI in a Sandbox Physics Game (Stage 2, 8:17 AM). *Seyedahmad Rahimi, University of Florida; Salah Esmailigoujar, University of Florida; Hongming Li, University of Florida*

The Impact of Test Preparation on Cognitive Abilities Testing with Diverse Student Populations (Stage 2, 8:35 AM). *Debi K. Torres, Baylor University; Fatih Ozkan, Baylor University; Aysil Agaya, Baylor University*

The Impact of Comprehension-Focused Digital Reading on National Literacy Outcomes: Evidence from Seychelles (Stage 2, 8:44 AM). *Carol M Johnson, Renaissance Learning Inc. - Wisconsin Rapids, WI; Chris McKenzie, Renaissance Learning*

Shaping Young Minds: The Role of Growth Mindset in K–12 Language Learning Success. (Stage 2, 8:53 AM). *Ran Gao, University of Florida; Congzhi Ma, University of Florida; Loraine Cisternas-Garcia, University of Florida*

A Longitudinal Investigation of Achievement Emotions and Engagement in Chinese EFL SPOC-Based Blended Learning (Stage 2, 9:02 AM). *banban Li, University of Science and Technology Beijing*

Chair: *Jaekyung Lee, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

15.043. e-Lightning Ed-Talk Session 1 - Stage 3. AERA e-Lightning Ed-Talks; AERA Ed Talk
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Exhibit Hall A - Stage 3; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Advancing Future Social Capabilities: Exploring Theory of Mind Training for Autism Spectrum Disorder — a Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis (Stage 3, 7:50 AM). *Huan Huang, East China Normal University; Sheng Xu, East China Normal University*

Environmental Indicators of Engagement Tool: Development, Preliminary Technical Adequacy, and Initial Field Experiences (Stage 3, 7:59 AM). *Jeong Hoon Choi, University of Kansas; Allyson Satter, University of Kansas; Sheila Wells-Moreaux, University of Kansas; Karmen Clark, University of Kansas*

Transforming EFL Learning: The Promise and Challenges of

Generative AI Integration in Higher Education (Stage 3, 8:08 AM). *Siyuan Chen, College of William & Mary*

Generative AI as Pedagogical Partner: Adoption, Challenges, and Transformation in U.S. Language Classrooms (Stage 3, 8:17 AM). *Jue Wang, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Kristin Davin, University of North Carolina - Charlotte*

Investigating Student Engagement and Ethical Reflection through Generative AI in Graduate Instructional Design (Stage 3, 8:50 AM). *Scott H. Moss, National University; Dwayne Wood, National University*

Moving Beyond Efficiency: How Teacher Educators Reconsidered Their Beliefs and Practices with Generative AI (Stage 3, 8:59 AM). *Luqing Zang, Slippery Rock University of Pennsylvania; Jingwen He, University of North Texas; Yesim Nur Akar Hozman, Michigan State University*

Chair: *Jessica Nina Lester, Indiana University*

Wednesday, April 8th, 8:00 am

16.010. Chinese American Educational Research and Development Association Annual Meeting. Affiliated Groups; Panel Discussion
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Boyle Heights; 8:00am to 2:00pm

16.011. Chinese American Educational Research and Development Association Annual Meeting. Affiliated Groups; Panel Discussion
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Ladera Heights; 8:00am to 2:00pm

16.012. Society for the Study of Curriculum History Annual Meeting (Day 2). Affiliated Groups; Panel Discussion
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 6th Floor, Broadway; 8:00am to 12:00pm

Chair: *Simon N. Jorgenson, University of Vermont*

Wednesday, April 8th, 8:45 am

Committee Sessions

17.010. Graduate Student Welcome Orientation. Graduate Student Council; Reception
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 502A; 8:45-10:15am

Chair: *Edith P. Middleton, Teachers College, Columbia University*
Participants: *Cammie Justus-Smith, Virginia Commonwealth University; Marjorie M. Hahn, Stanford University; Mark Wilson, University of Houston*

Wednesday, April 8th, 9:00 am

AERA Related Activities

18.010. AERA Research Engagement and Development With Youth (READY) Program Session 1 (Invitation Only).

AERA Related Activities; Invited Speaker Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Room 306AB; 9:00am to 8:00pm

Chair: *Lori Diane Hill, American Educational Research Association*

Wednesday, April 8th, 9:30 am

19.010. zzzzzCancelled Per email 3-19-26 Korean American Educational Researcher Association. Affiliated Groups; Seminar
Westin Bonaventure, Level 3, Emerald Bay; 9:30am to 5:30pm

Wednesday, April 8th, 9:45 am

Presidential Sessions

20.010. Building the World Anew: Historically-Responsive Educational Approaches Towards just and Sustainable Climate Futures. AERA Presidential Session; Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 406AB; 9:45-11:15am

Chair: *Christina Hewko, Stanford University*

Participants: *Christopher Jadallah, University of California - Los Angeles; Michelle Hernandez Romero, University of California - Los Angeles; Lauren Arzaga Daus, University of California - Los Angeles; Sara Jasmin Diaz-Montejano, University of California - Los Angeles; Ananda M. Marin, University of California - Los Angeles; Sara E. Tolbert, Monash University; Fikile Nxumalo, University of Toronto - OISE; Tia C. Madkins, The University of Texas at Austin*

Discussant: *Déana A Scipio, IslandWood*

Committee Sessions

20.011. (Re)membering the History of World War II from the Asian Theater. International Relations Committee; Invited

Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 402A; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Teaching Difficult Knowledge of World War II through Chinese History Textbooks. *Chenyu Li, Indiana University - South Bend*

Remembering and Silencing: (Re)presentations of World War II in Korean National Curriculum and Textbooks. *Jongsung Kim, Hiroshima University; Sunun Park, Cheongju National University of Education*

Challenging Narratives of the “Good War”: Filipino Perspectives of World War II. *Theresa Alviar Martin, Kennesaw State University*

Chair: *Lin Wu, Western Oregon University*

Discussant: *Sohyun An, Kennesaw State University*

International Organization Sessions

20.012. Comparative Research on Artificial Intelligence in Education. International Aligned

Organizations/International Academy of Education - IAE; Symposium

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum A; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Artificial Intelligence and Education in the Global South: A Systems Perspective. *Fernando M. Reimers, Harvard University; Zainab Azim, Harvard University; Maria-Renée Palomo, International Education Researcher & Consultant; Callysta Thony, International Education Researcher & Consultant*

The Relationship Between AI Chatbot Use, Student Performance on Domain-Specific Assessments, and Learning Outcomes in Higher Education: A Case-study from Germany. *Olga Zlatkin Troitschanskaia, Johannes Gutenberg University of Mainz; Denis Federiak, Johannes Gutenberg University of Mainz; Dimitri Molerov, Humboldt University of Berlin*

Leveraging AI and Teacher Expertise to Improve Students’ Science Explanations. *Marcia Linn, University of California - Berkeley*

Efficacy, Validity and Fairness Considerations in AI-Driven Assessments. *Kadriye Ercikan, Educational Testing Service*

Chair: *Ee Ling Low, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University*

Discussant: *Jonathan David Jansen, Stellenbosch University*

Division Sessions

20.013. Leadership for Multilingual and Immigrant Students and Communities. Division A - Administration; Paper

Session

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, La Brea; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Critical Intersections in Leading Dual Language Bilingual Education. *Elena Izquierdo, University of Texas - El Paso; Vanessa Espitia Mendoza, University of Texas - El Paso; Sarah De La Garza, Texas Tech University; Jose Medina, Educational Solutions*

Constructing a Future for Multilingual Learners: A Framework for Linguistically Responsive Leadership. *Mathew O'Ryan Espinosa-Castro, California State University - Sacramento*

How a Leadership Institute Supports District Leaders in Equitable English Learners Reclassification. *Soomin Chao, California State University - Fullerton; Amanda R. Diaz, California State University - Fullerton*

A Meta-Synthesis of the Educational Leadership Practices for Improving Latinx Immigrant Student (LIS) Success. *Fangsu Li, University of Alabama*

Leading for Learning, Wellbeing and Belonging: Synthesizing Practices from 110 Educators Supporting Refugee and Asylum-Seeking Communities Across Five Countries. *Scott R. Imig, University of Newcastle; Maura Sellars, University of Newcastle, NSW; Doug Rowley Imig, Friends of the Future*

Discussant: *Cristina Alfaro, San Diego State University*

20.014. Student-Focused Leadership for Equity and Justice.

Division A - Administration; Paper Session

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Los Cerritos; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Deepening Understandings of Collective Leadership Practices that Support Black Student Success. *Jason Salisbury, University of Illinois at Chicago; Decoteau J. Irby, University of Illinois at Chicago; Devin Swartley, Chicago Public Schools; David Mayrowetz, University of Illinois at Chicago*

Leading while Black in Crisis: Unforgetting Histories and Envisioning Culturally Responsive Futures in P-12 Education. *Jennifer R. Esposito, Georgia State University; Dionne Cowan, Georgia State University*

The Role of School Leaders in Transforming Experiences, Engagement, and Opportunities for Black Student Excellence. *Diana A. Porras, California State University - Long Beach; Cara Richards-Tutor, California State University - Long Beach; Jolan Smith, California State University - Long Beach; Vanessa Placeres, San Diego State University; Caroline Lopez-Perry, California State University - Long Beach*

Affirming Identities, Building Community: Culturally Responsive School Leadership Practices That Support LGBTQ-Parent Families. *Gerald Maraia, Brooklyn College - CUNY*

School Principals' Practices for Social Justice: The Case of

Students Facing the Threat of Home Demolition or

Relocation. *Rima'a Da'as, Hebrew University of Jerusalem; Shorok Suliman, Hebrew University of Jerusalem*

Chair: *Lisa Bass, North Carolina State University*

Discussant: *Patience Amadu, University of Colorado - Colorado Springs*

20.015. Politics of Affect: The Technologies of Governance in Making Normative Subjectivities in Education. Division B - Curriculum Studies; Symposium

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304A; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Cruel Optimism in Teacher Education: Governing Teacher Professionalism Through Affective Infrastructures and Technologies of Patience. *Sun Young Lee, Wichita State University; Soo Bin Jang, University of Delaware*

Governing through feeling(s): The affective-discursive politics of high school education reform in South Korea. *Soohan Lee, Seoul National University; Kyunghye So, Seoul National University*

Understanding Affect for Political Governance: Infantile Citizenship Through Visuals in Korean Colonial History Education. *Younsun Choi, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Managing Difference through Affective Economies: Governing Multicultural Subjectivities of Happiness and Anxiety in South Korean Education. *Ji Hyun Hwang, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Making playful self: Fabricating "the abnormal" in joyfulness. *Chushan Wu, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Chair: *Bernadette Baker, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Discussants: *Kathryn J. Strom, California State University - East Bay; YANMEI WU, Hebei Normal University*

20.016. Advancing Math Motivation, Engagement and Persistence: Insights from Digital Interventions and Research-Practice Partnerships. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Structured Poster Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 515A; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

1. Supporting Collaboration and Co-navigating Tensions around Motivation, Engagement, and Persistence in Mathematics Education within a Collaboratory (Poster 1). *Corinne Singleton, Menlo Education Research; Britte Haugan Cheng, Menlo Education Research; Ann Edwards, West Ed; Tiffany L Clark, Menlo Education Research*
2. Co-Designing Digital Clinical Simulations with Students of Color to Support Equitable Mathematics Instruction (Poster 2). *Pelin Jackson, Boston University; Juliana Isabela Ayala, Boston University; Arielle Vargas, Boston University; Gregory Benoit, Boston University; Erin Barno, ETS*
3. What are Student Designers taking away from the Process of

Making AEM Sims (Poster 3). *Pelin Jackson, Boston University; Juliana Isabela Ayala, Boston University; Arielle Vargas, Boston University; Gregory Benoit, Boston University; Erin Barno, ETS*

4. Use of a Collaborative Digital Math Curriculum to Teach for Belonging and Engagement (Poster 4). *Sara McAlister, New York University; Erika Abarca Millán, New York University*
5. Digital Math Curriculum to Foster Belonging and Engagement: Teacher Moves and Student Outcomes (Poster 5). *John Sludden, New York University; Cheri Fancsali, Research Alliance for New York City Schools*
6. Enhancing Engagement and Learning Through Interactive Conceptual Learning Tools for Mathematics (Poster 6). *Steven Ritter, Carnegie Learning, Inc.; April Murphy, Carnegie Learning, Inc.*
7. From Exit Tickets to End-of-Year Outcomes: Predictive Validity of AI-Scored Student Work in Middle School Math (Poster 7). *Selena Castro, EdLight; Teryn Thomas, EdLight; Nathaniel Schwartz, Brown University; Kate Larned, Annenberg Institute at Brown University; Yuno Hamaguchi, Annenberg Institute at Brown University; Olga Pagán, RPPL, Annenberg Institute at Brown University; Michel Meneses, EdLight; Lindsay Looft, EdLight*

Chair: *Sara McAlister, New York University*

20.017. Messages, Pedagogies, and Identities: Building Belonging for Diverse Learners. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Level 2, Mt. Washington; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Higher Education is Complex: Exploring the Dynamic Interplay among Belonging, Competence Beliefs, Role Identity, and Achievement in Engineering Students. *William Van Luven, Michigan State University; Garam A. Lee, Michigan State University; Utku Caybas, Michigan State University; Saki Inoue, Michigan State University; Marissa N Taylor, University of Michigan; Hyein Jee, Michigan State University; René Gerardo Pérez Melgar, Michigan State University; S. Patrick Walton, Michigan State University; Lisa Linnenbrink-Garcia, Michigan State University*

Investigating How Asset-Based Pedagogy Shapes University Student Belongingness and Experiences of Racial Microaggressions. *Katherine C. Cheng, University of Arizona; Nathaniel Jerry Gallegos, University of Arizona; Alicia Jane Peras, University of Arizona; Thomas Chong, University of Arizona*

Math Belonging and STEM Persistence: The Long-Term Impact of Early High School Experiences. *Piper Stanger, California Department of Education; Sandra Graham, University of California - Los Angeles*

The Right Messages from the Right Messengers: Increasing Girls' Interest in Coding with Peer Videos. *Summer Robinson, University of Houston; Kahyun Lee, University of*

Houston; Jennifer L. Thompson, University of Houston; Taylor Alexander, Digital Promise; Shaila Sharmin, University of Houston; Andrew N. Meltzoff, University of Washington; Sapna Cheryan, University of Washington - Seattle; Weihua Fan, University of Houston; Allison Master, University of Houston

Too hot, too cold, or just right? Motivational Microclimates and Correlates in Three STEM Courses. *Kristy A. Robinson, McGill University; Jessica Hunter, McGill University; Cole D. Johnson, McGill University; Sanheeta Shankar, McGill University*

Chair: *Sanheeta Shankar, McGill University*

Discussant: *Chris Rozek, Washington University in St. Louis*

20.018. Promoting Equitable Learning and Career Pathways in STEM Through Positive Youth Development. Division E - Counseling and Human Development; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 301B;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

From Opportunity Gap to Yield: The Benefits of OST Mentored Research for Youth in STEM. *Karen Hammerness*
The Development of Science Identity Through Near Peer Mentoring and Research Experiences. *Ross C. Anderson, Creative Engagement Lab*

Incorporating the Social, Cultural, and Emotional Dimensions of Student Learning to Develop STEM-identities in Computer Science. *Stanley L. Johnson, University of California - Los Angeles*

Developmental Relationships as a Critical Lever for Equitable Math Learning. *Lauren Rice, Latino Student Fund*

Chair: *Christina Cipriano, Yale University*

Discussant: *Jeremy Jay Taylor, Collaborative for Academic, Social, and Emotional Learning*

20.019. Learning from Educators who have used the Profession as an Act of Resistance. Division F - Historical Inquiry in Education; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 504;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Blackboards and Barbed Wire: Reconsidering the Teachers of Japanese Americans at the Minidoka Concentration Camp Schools. *Abigail Jean Kahn, Stanford University*

The Sooner State and Sanctions: A Retrospective of Oklahoma's Educator Revolt of 1963-1965. *Don C. Murray, Oklahoma State University; Hannah-Scout Hossaini Anvar, Oklahoma State University; AJ Tierney, Oklahoma State University*

"We Ain't New to this, We True to This": Teaching Democracy and Citizenship: Through Black Educator Oral and Life Histories. *Brandon J. Beck, University of Maryland Baltimore County*

Marginalised Broker of Educational Reform? Micropolitics,

Pedagogical Hierarchies, and a Forgotten Educator in Republican China. *Wei Li, KU Leuven*

Teaching Against Empire: Black Educational Resistance and Repurposed Spaces Across the British Empire. *Esther Anfo-Whyte, Harvard University; Darien Dey, Harvard University*

Chair: *M. Nathan Tanner, University of Nevada - Reno*

Discussant: *Chara H. Bohan, Georgia State University*

20.020. Beyond Binary Thinking: Jews, Antisemitism, and Navigating Difference. Division G - Social Context of Education; Symposium

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 303B; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Introducing and Critiquing HebCrit: A Framework for Understanding and Combating Antisemitism and Jew-Hate. *Noah D. Drezner, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Invisibilized: Being a White Jew in the Space. *Jennifer Goldstein, California State University - Fullerton*

Allyship & Audience: Jewish Inclusion and Combating Antisemitism in Elementary Teacher Education. *Keitha-Gail Martin-Kerr, University of Minnesota; Jana Lo Bello Miller, University of Minnesota*

Towards a Liberatory Future: Thinking with and Beyond Oppression and Intersectionality Frameworks. *Majida Kargbo, Northwestern University*

Chair: *Jennifer Goldstein, California State University - Fullerton*

Discussant: *Benjamin M. Jacobs, The George Washington University*

20.021. Count Me In: An HBCU P-20 Research-Practice Partnership to Build Math Teacher Pathways. Division G - Social Context of Education; Symposium

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 303A; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

The Southern Initiative Algebra Project: Coordinating Community, School, and University Partnerships for Math Teacher Development. *David J. Dennis, Southern Initiative Algebra Project*

Leveraging Research Practice Partnerships to Build HBCU Faculty Capacity to Research the Teacher Pipeline. *Latara O. Lampkin, Heritage University*

Co-creating the Math Education Curriculum and the Jackson Center for Excellence in Teacher Preparation. *Tony T. Latiker, Jackson State University*

Challenges to Evaluating a Collaborative, Dual Enrollment Program Designed to Address Teacher Shortages in Jackson, MS. *Sam Mozee, Jackson State University*

Chair: *Deidre L. Wheaton, Jackson State University*

Discussant: *Deidre L. Wheaton, Jackson State University*

20.022. Reparative Educational Futures: Reimagining Futures through Historical Consciousness and Anti-Colonial

Praxis. Division G - Social Context of Education; Symposium

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 301A; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Interrogating, Disrupting, and Dismantling the Cycle of Racism: The Importance of Historical and Structural Consciousness/Thinking. *Osly J. Flores, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

The Reparative Materials and Possibilities Embedded within Slavery Heritage Sites. *Eric Kyere, Indiana University*

Improvement Science as Decolonizing Praxis: Shifting Decolonization from Discourse to Action. *Edwin Nii Bonney, Clemson University*

Chair: *Mama Adobea Nii Owoo, McGill University*

Discussant: *Mama Adobea Nii Owoo, McGill University*

20.023. Beyond the Grade: Advancing Equity through Assessment Reform and Analytic Innovation. Division H - Research, Evaluation and Assessment in Schools; Working Group Roundtable

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 501A; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

A Mediocrity Trap as Symbolic Violence: Re-examining Teachers' Stereotype in Student Evaluation. *Minda Tan, Shandong Normal University; Liangliang Cai, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Senior High School Teachers' Knowledge, Beliefs, and Practices of Performance-Based Assessment. *Ebenezer Takyi-Wadieh, Ohio University; Regina Nugba, University of Cape Coast; George Oduro-Okyireh, Akenten Appiah-Minkah University; Enoch Tsey, University of Cape Coast; Philip Nartey, Holy Child College of Education*

Uncovering Intersectional Inequalities in Academic Growth: Applying MAIHDA to Student Growth Scores within School-Level Contexts. *Kent Seidel, University of Colorado - Denver; Julie R. OBrian-Oxenford, University of Colorado - Denver*

Unforgetting Grading Inequities: Examining Grade Distribution Stability After Comprehensive Assessment and Reporting Changes. *Laura J. Link, University of North Dakota; Radomir Ray Mitic, College of William & Mary; Maureen P. Leeson, Bethlehem Area School District; Joseph R. Anthes, Bethlehem Area School District*

Discussant: *Dustin Sonny James Van Orman, Western Washington University*

20.024. Precision Education and Coaching in the Professions: Translating Early Promise into Ethical, Equitable Implementation. Division I - Education in the Professions; Symposium

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum D; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Utilizing AI with Community Coaching and Capacity Building to Improve Team-Based Learning Design and Readiness. *Kadian McIntosh, University of Arizona; Jennifer Wishnie, University of Arizona; Jennifer Bouschor, University of Arizona; Laura Roberts, University of Arizona; Daniel Johnson, University of Arizona; Brisa Hsieh, University of Arizona; Stephanie Shaver, University of Arizona; Sallianne Schlacks, University of Arizona; Chris Hauser, University of Arizona; Zachary Boeder, University of Arizona; Holly Bender, University of Arizona; Patricia Beyers Pelzel, University of Arizona*

Advancing Family Medicine Maintenance of Certification Through LLM Powered Adaptive Learning Feedback . *Ting Wang, American Board of Family Medicine*

Postphenomenological Insights into Trainee-AI Interaction: Reimagining the Promise of Precision Education. *Ahreum Lim, Arizona State University; Nathaniel Kim, University of Arizona*

Assessing the Assessor: Evaluating Feedback from an Open-Source “Virtual Preceptor” to Promote Critical Thinking. *Kuan Xing, University of Iowa; Flávia Oliveira, Centro Universitário de Mineiros (UNIFIMES); Lukas Shum-Tim, McMaster University; Pooja Varman, Case Western Reserve University; Matthew Kaminsky, University of Chicago; Xiaomei Song, Case Western Reserve University; Brian Christopher Gin, University of Illinois at Chicago*

Feedback and Coaching in MedEdPORTAL (2005–2025): Insights to Advance Assessment in Precision Medical Education. *EunMi Park, HRDE; Gary J. Confessore, Human Resource Development Enterprises*

Chairs: *Brian Christopher Gin, University of Illinois at Chicago; Kuan Xing, University of Iowa*

Discussant: *Monica M. Cuddy, NBME*

20.025. Navigating graduate education and opportunities.

Division J - Postsecondary Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum G; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

A Multi-Level Exploration of Imposter Phenomenon in Graduate Students in the U.S. *Musbah Shaheen, University of Massachusetts - Amherst*

Navigating Kazakhstani graduate students’ intercultural citizenship development and future vision in Türkiye. *Anas Hajar; Ahmet Aypay, Nazarbayev University; Murat Özdemir, Anadolu University*

RISE-UP in California: Reimagining Graduate Student Success Through Place-Based, Healing-Centered, and Equity-Driven Futures. *Marcella Cardoza McCollum, San Jose State University; Melisa Kaye, San Jose State University*

Zine-ing Latinidad: Zinemaking, Latinidades, and the Muxerista Pedagogical Possibilities with/ in the Graduate Classroom. *Pablo Montes, Texas Christian University; Jose*

Omar Serna, Texas Christian University; Garrison Daly, Texas Christian University; Maria O'Connor, Texas Christian University; Katherine Crowe, Texas Christian University; Anna Block, Texas Christian University

Discussant: *Rachel L. Renbarger, FHI 360*

20.026. Negotiating Progress: Postsecondary Faculty Development, Collaboration, and Governance. Division J

- Postsecondary Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum H; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Curriculum Change as Collective Work: Understanding Graduate-Level Curricular Reform in Computing at Minority-Serving Institutions. *Annie M. Wofford, Florida State University; Morgan Danyi, Florida State University; Lara Perez-Felkner, Florida State University*

Supporting Acceleration of Research Translation (ART): Diagnosing and Fulfilling the Needs of ART Awardee Institutions. *Jesenia Rosales, Oregon State University; Rachael Ann Cody, Oregon State University; Purim Junkham, Oregon State University; Jana Bouwma-Gearhart, Oregon State University*

Faculty Autonomy and Academic Freedom in Democratic Education: Comparative Perspectives from Mexico and the United States. *Jenifer Crawford, University of Southern California; Elida Sanchez-Cruz, Universidad Veracruzana; Isai Ali Guevara Bazan, Universidad Veracruzana; Jorge Martinez Cortes, Universidad Veracruzana*

Dilemmas in Collaborative Governance of Non-degree Education in Chinese Colleges and Universities. *Yifan ZHAO, Shanghai Polytechnic University; Leilin Yu, Shanghai Polytechnic University*

20.027. Neurodivergent and Disability Discourse in Higher Education. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum F; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Disability on campus: How do individual and college environment factors predict levels of disability disclosure? *Madeline Celeste O'Grady, University of Texas at Austin; Stephanie W. Cawthon, University of Texas at Austin; Maura J. Borrego, University of Texas at Austin*

Predictors of Postsecondary Enrollment for Students with Disabilities: A Scoping Review Using a Social-Ecological Lens. *Eunice K Kim, University of California - Los Angeles*
Creating a Safe Space Within Safe Spaces: Nestled Support for Neurodivergent Students at an HBCU. *Elizabeth Holliday Morgan, Morgan State University; Simone Gibson, Morgan State University; Winifred Winston, So All Can Read; Leslie A. Anderson, Morgan State University*

Chair: *Malik M. Wali Awan, Indiana University*

Discussant: *Janelle A. Johnson, North Carolina State University*

20.028. Unveiling Campus Racial Realities: Faculty and Staff Voices from National Assessment of Collegiate Campus Climate Survey. Division J - Postsecondary Education;

Symposium

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum I;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Supporting While Marginalized: Racial Realities and Institutional Responsibility in Student Affairs. *Jihye Kwon, University of Southern California; Rodolfo Andy Nunez, University of Southern California*

Performing Equity, Perpetuating Harm: Counternarratives of Black Staff on DEI and Anti-Blackness. *Royel M. Johnson, University of Southern California; Alexia Oduro, University of Southern California; Marcus Maximus Martin, University of Southern California*

Examining faculty race-consciousness: Findings and Implications for Practice. *Debbie Hanson, University of Southern California; Jihye Kwon, University of Southern California; Esmeralda A. Hernandez-Hamed, University of Southern California*

Chair: *Jihye Kwon, University of Southern California*

Discussant: *Royel M. Johnson, University of Southern California*

20.029. Racialized Emotions, Trauma, and the Ethics of Feeling in Teacher Education. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Symposium

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 6;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

You Can't Heal What You Won't Feel': Centering Emotions as Embodiment as Trauma-Informed Praxis. *Sharim Hannegan-Martinez, University of Michigan*

At the Frontlines of Healing: Educator Perspectives on Addressing Racial Stress and Trauma in Schools. *Sophie D'Souza, Stanford University; Farzana Tabitha Saleem Adjah, Stanford University; Lionel Howard, The George Washington University*

Teaching with a Racialized Heart: Reclaiming Emotion as Theory and Praxis in Trauma-Informed Education. *Adam J. Alvarez, Texas A&M University; Cheryl E. Matias, University of San Diego*

Chair: *Cheryl E. Matias, University of San Diego*

Discussant: *Tyrone C. Howard, University of California - Los Angeles*

20.030. Transformative Practices in Teacher Education: Lessons from the U.S. and China. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Symposium

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum C; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Rethinking the Purposes of Teaching: An Incremental PAR in Chinese Free Teacher Education Programs. *Xin Xiang, Harvard University; Wenjie Wang, Beijing Normal University; Haoqi Li, Beijing Normal University; Yipeng Guo, Beijing Normal University; Jianbo Lin, Beijing Normal University; Yuxuan Wu, Beijing Normal University; Sihan Shen, Beijing Normal University*

Transforming Teacher Recruitment for Urban STEM Excellence: Lessons for Traditional Preparation Programs. *Roland Sintos Coloma, Wayne State University*

Can We See It? Making Culturally Sustaining Pedagogy Visible in Practice. *Jennifer M. Lewis, Wayne State University*

Curriculum and Pedagogy in the Classroom: Daily Learners as a Teacher Inquiry Model. *Jun Teng, Beijing Normal University; Ruoshi Li, Beijing Normal University; Jurong Zhang, National Compulsory Education Teaching Reform Pilot Zone Wujiang Office, Jiangsu Province, China; Min Yu, Wayne State University; Christopher B. Crowley, Wayne State University; Xin Xiang, Harvard University; Chenhui Gao, Beijing Normal University*

Archives in the Classroom and Community: Transforming Teacher Education through Critical Archival Engagement. *Min Yu, Wayne State University; Christopher B. Crowley, Wayne State University; Meghan Courtney, University of Michigan; Dan Golodner, Wayne State University*

Chair: *Christopher B. Crowley, Wayne State University*

Discussant: *A. Lin Goodwin, Boston College*

20.031. Unforgetting our Language Inheritance: Imagining Multilingual Teacher Education Futures in the Midwest.

Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 1;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Linguistic Responsiveness and Teacher Education Futurities: A Context-based Case Study in Curricular and Programmatic Transformation. *Victoria F. Trinder, University of Illinois at Chicago*

Creating Critical Language Educators through Cariño via the Higher Education Classroom. *P. Zitlali Morales, University of Illinois at Chicago*

"Makes Me Feel Poderosa": Conversando in Spanish in the Bilingual Teacher Education Classroom de la Ciudad de los Vientos. *Jose Garcia, University of Illinois at Chicago*

Unforgetting Language Inheritance and Building Raiz Pedagogy Futures. *Zitlaltoka Ramirez Huerta, University of Illinois at Chicago*

Elevating the Spanish Language Through a Linguistic Justice Leadership Coaching Approach. *Sylvia Ibarra Delgado, University of Illinois at Chicago*

Chair: *Enrique Aleman, Trinity University*

Discussant: *Angela Valenzuela, University of Texas at Austin*

20.032. Expanding Our Understanding: Research on Rural Community School Implementation. Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 2;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- Evolving Community Schools Implementation in Rural Vermont. *Peter N. Knox, University of Vermont*
- Advancing Rural Community Schools through University-Assisted Community School Partnerships. *Janine Al-Aseer, University of Tennessee; Jerry Johnson, East Carolina University*
- What Does it Mean to be a Community School? Voices From Kentucky. *Amanda U. Potterton, University of Kentucky; Zitsi Mirakhur, University of Kentucky; Shannon O. Sampson, University of Kentucky; Kelly D. Bradley, Marshall University; Isaiah Moore, University of Kentucky*
- Banding Together: Building Cross-District and Cross-County Partnerships to Leverage Resources in Rural California. *Emily Germain, Learning Policy Institute; Laura E. Hernandez, Learning Policy Institute*

Chair: *Rebecca S. Levine, University of California - San Diego*
Discussant: *Tiffany Miller, Learning Policy Institute*

20.033. Whose Histories? Whose Futures? Coloniality, Control, and Counterstories in Schooling. Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 10; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- Connectivity As Praxis: (Re)Thinking Critical Policy Analysis with Theories of De/coloniality. *Rachel Lockart, Augustana College*
- Countering the Backlash: High School Alumni Reflect on the Power of Racial Justice Education. *Rebecca Novalis-Edwards, Loyola Marymount University*
- “A Legacy of Strength and Brilliance”: Black Educators’ Resistance and Resilience Amid Antidemocratic Legislation. *Debra A Jones, The Ohio State University*
- One State’s Historical and Contemporary Resistance and Obstruction to Landmark Federal Education for Equitable Education Reform. *Sheryl Jones Croft, Kennesaw State University; Michelle A. Purdy, Washington University in St. Louis*
- A Risk Revealed: A Critical Discourse Analysis of A Nation at Risk. *Dre’Sha T. Singleton, North Carolina State University*

Chair: *Mariam Yasmine Noura Jeanne N’diaye, Pennsylvania State University*

Discussant: *Jawanza Kalonji Rand, Teachers College, Columbia University*

20.034. Learning from Implementation Research: How Curriculum, Professional Learning, AI Tools and Classroom Studies Can Support AI-Literacy. SIG-Advanced Technologies for Learning; Symposium
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Santa Barbara C; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- Paper 1: Using Implementation Data to Improve a Curricular Unit to Develop AI Literacy. *William R. Penuel, University of Colorado - Boulder; Mon-Lin Ko, University of Colorado - Boulder; Nga Hoang, University of Colorado - Boulder; Brooklyn Clines, University of Colorado - Boulder*
- Paper 2: Designing Professional Learning to Support Transdisciplinary AI Adaptations. *Nga Hoang, University of Colorado - Boulder; Mon-Lin Ko, University of Colorado - Boulder; William R. Penuel, University of Colorado - Boulder; Collette Heskett, University of Colorado - Boulder*
- Paper 3: Classroom Studies: How Does an AI partner Influence Small Group Collaboration? *Mon-Lin Ko, University of Colorado - Boulder; Jason Reitman, University of Colorado - Boulder; Brooklyn Clines, University of Colorado - Boulder; Sierra Rose, University of Colorado - Boulder; Emily Watts, University of Colorado - Boulder; Chelsea Chandler, University of Colorado - Boulder; Peter W. Foltz, University of Colorado - Boulder*
- Paper 4: Classroom Studies: Expanding our Understanding of Collaboration Through Analysis of Nonverbals in Small Group Interactions. *Indrani Dey, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Collette Heskett, University of Colorado - Boulder; Mon-Lin Ko, University of Colorado - Boulder*
- Paper 5: Learning Outcomes: Fostering AI Literacy Through Human-AI Moderation Systems Evaluation in Middle School Classrooms. *Nga Hoang, University of Colorado - Boulder; Collette Heskett, University of Colorado - Boulder; Mon-Lin Ko, University of Colorado - Boulder; William R. Penuel, University of Colorado - Boulder; Julia Eden, University of Colorado - Boulder*

Chair: *Mon-Lin Ko, University of Colorado - Boulder*

Discussant: *Christopher J. Dede, Harvard University*

20.035. Adorning Futures: Embodied Aesthetics as Lived Curricula for Unforgetting and Futuring Education. SIG-Arts-Based Educational Research; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304C;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- Offering 1: Curating a Feminist of Color Pedagogy of Adornment. *Grace D. Player, University of Connecticut*
- Offering 2: Metaphysical Blackness and the Ontological Futuring of Black Youth Aesthetics. *Justin A. Coles, University of Massachusetts - Amherst*
- Offering 3: A Grammar of Black Livingness: Black Queer and Trans Youths’ Everyday Adornments as Literacy Performance. *monét cooper, University of Michigan*

SIG Sessions

Offering 4: Inventing New Worlds: Channeling Black Girl
Aesthetic & Imagination. *Courtney Mauldin-Jones, Syracuse
University*

Chair: *Grace D. Player, University of Connecticut*

Discussant: *Ruth Nicole Brown, Michigan State University*

**20.036. The Wages of Blackness: Black Women and Women of
Color in the Academy.** SIG-Critical Examination of Race,
Ethnicity, Class and Gender in Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 3;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

The Price of Representation: Black Faculty Wages and the
Myth of Meritocracy. *Jemimah L Young, Texas A&M
University; Kristian Edosomwan, University of Houston;
Dalvin Trevon Dunn, Texas A&M University*

“The department doesn't see me”: Interrogating departmental
climate. *Daisy Rodriguez, Pennsylvania State University;
LaWanda W. Ward, Pennsylvania State University*

Outmaneuvering Academic Landmines: Gendered Literacies as
Survival Maps for Black Women in the Academy. *Shalander
L. Samuels, Kean University; Azaria I. Cunningham, Boston
University; Candice Peters, Appalachian State University*

What the Syllabus Didn't Say: A Scholarly Personal Narrative
of a Black Woman's Invisible Labor in Graduate Education.
Katrina A Calhoun, University of Massachusetts - Amherst

Rooted in Resistance, Raised in Legacy: Black Women
Students Leading at Hispanic Serving Institutions. *Shanelle
A Watkins, University of California - San Diego*

Chair: *Alexis Morgan Young, Michigan State University*

Discussant: *Jemimah L Young, Texas A&M University*

**20.037. Critical Analyses of Identity, Belonging, and Racialized
Educational Outcomes.** SIG-Critical Quantitative
Methodologies; Paper Session
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Echo
Park; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Becoming a Researcher: A Critical Multiphase Mixed Methods
Study of Identity and Efficacy among Graduate Students of
Color. *Monica Hernandez-Johnson, University of Nevada -
Las Vegas*

Examining Racial Variation in Advising Program Outcomes
Through LASSO Modeling. *Gloria A. Segovia, University of
Illinois at Chicago; George Karabatsos, University of
Illinois at Chicago*

Revealing Gaps in Belonging in Incoming College Freshmen:
An Intersectional MAIHDA Analysis. *Anwasha Guha,
University of Oregon*

Understanding Heterogeneity in Outcomes Across Asian
Student Groups in the Introductory Physics Courses. *Iy Le,
Iowa State University; Grace Angell, Iowa State University;
Jayson Nissen, Montana State University; Ben Van Dusen,
Iowa State University*

Understanding Inequities in Teaching Performance Assessment
Results: The Role of Pathways, Programs, and Supports.

*Susan Kemper Patrick, Learning Policy Institute; Lillie Ko-
Wong, University of California - San Diego*

Chair: *Rebecca A. Cruz, Johns Hopkins University*

Discussant: *Mengyuan Liang, University of Chicago*

20.038. Intersectionalities. SIG-Deaf and Hard of Hearing
Intersectionalities and Perspectives; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 501C;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Signed Interview Methods for Research with Deaf and Hard of
Hearing Youth. *Kristabel Stark, University of Vermont; John
S. Pirone, University of Vermont; Brittney Staffieri,
University of Vermont*

Providing a Deaf-centric Space to Promote Signing Deaf
Adolescents' Language, Identity, and Social-emotional
Development. *John S. Pirone, University of Vermont;
Kristabel Stark, University of Vermont*

Teaching Literacy to Deaf and Hard of Hearing in Chile:
Strategies From Educational Professional. *Angela Hinojosa,
University of Florida*

A Black Deaf Woman's Reflections on Peace Corps Deaf
Education. *Nicole Mapp, University of California - Santa
Barbara*

Brazilian Sign Language and Teacher Education: Analysing the
Syllabus Based on Decolonial Perspective. *Thais Carvalho,
Universidade Federal de Viçosa; Ana Luisa Borba Gediell,
Federal University of Viçosa*

Chair: *Colleen L. Smith, California State University - Northridge*

Discussant: *Marlon H. Kuntze, California School for the Deaf*

20.039. The Scholarship of Teaching Evaluation. SIG-Faculty
Teaching, Evaluation, and Development; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 7;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Calibrating Course Evaluations: Student Self-Reported Effort
as a Lens for Faculty Development. *Mark Urtel, UII - PE
267*

Evaluating systematic bias in faculty course evaluations:
Results from an extensive university-wide evaluation.
*Courtney Donovan, University of Colorado - Denver;
Dennis DeBay, University of Colorado - Denver; Abbey
Eversole, University of Colorado - Denver; Chelsea
Sobczak, University of Colorado - Denver; Cristina
Gillanders, University of Colorado - Denver; Jennifer
Camacho Taylor, University of Colorado - Denver; Maren
Scull, University of Colorado - Denver*

Relationships Between Students' Motivational Climate
Perceptions and Their Evaluations of Teaching in a
University Course. *Saylor Bane, Virginia Tech; Brett D.
Jones, Virginia Tech*

Student Evaluations of Teaching: Latent Topics and its Differences by Race/Ethnicity and Gender. *Tai Junior Taliaoa, New York University*

20.040. Transforming Postdoctoral and Early Career

Pathways. SIG-Graduate and Postdoctoral Education across the Disciplines; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 8;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

A Postdoctoral Program Model: Reimagining Merit, Mentorship, and Cultural Wealth. *Mariam Manuel, University of Houston; April L. Peters-Hawkins, University of Houston; David Horton, Jr., University of Houston; Jerrod Henderson, University of Houston*

Golden Ticket or Great Trade-Off? Exploring Career Experiences of International Postdocs in Chinese Universities. *Jiawen Xu, East China Normal University; Junwen Zhu, East China Normal University*

Impact of GenAI on PhD Graduates' Identity and Career Transition: A Longitudinal Case Study in Engineering Education. *Sichen Lai, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Yun Dai, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Ang Liu, University of New South Wales; Cher Ping Lim, The Education University of Hong Kong*

Unveiling the Hidden Pathways to Postdoc Job Satisfaction: An fsQCA Study of Motivational Factors. *Bing Xiaoyi, Hunan Normal University*

Chair: *Charlotte Hayes, Florida State University*

Discussant: *Deniece Dortch, The George Washington University*

20.041. Hip Hop, Identity, and Black Educational Futures.

SIG-Hip Hop Theories, Praxis & Pedagogies; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum B; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Hip-Hop Culture as a Catalyst for Belonging Among Black Male High School Students Who Stutter. *Antonio L. Ellis, American University; Chaz T. Gipson, U.S. Department of Education; Phelton Cortez Moss, Virginia Commonwealth University; Eugene Pringle, American University*

"I don't want to create a bunch of Michelle Pfeiffers": White Social Studies Teacher Educators' Racialized Understandings of Hip-Hop Education. *Kelly R. Allen, Augusta University*

Let Me Ride: Hip-Hop as a Poetics of Fugitive Refusal in Education. *Jeremy Divinity, N/A*

Standing On Business: Designing Agentic Futures with Justice-Impacted Black Male Youth. *Bianca J. Nightengale-Lee, Western Michigan University; Karika Ann Parker, Western Michigan University; Gus Calbert, Western Michigan University; Mariana Montserrat Bringas-Acevedo, Western Michigan University*

Teach like an MC: Hip-Hop Pedagogy as Black Liberatory

Practice. *Edmund S. Adjapong, Seton Hall University*
Chair: *Ian Levy, Rutgers University*

20.042. Advancing The Teaching and Learning of Collaborative Continuous Improvement in Education.

SIG-Improvement Science in Education; Structured Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 515B;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

1. Collaborative Continuous Improvement as Leadership Development in Early Childhood Programs (Poster 1). *John J. Hall, Independent Researcher; Shannon M. Calderone, Washington State University*
2. Using Collaborative Continuous Improvement to Build Capacity for Improving Student Belonging in a Research-to-Practice Model (Poster 2). *Katrina Struloeff, University of Pennsylvania; Megan MacDonald, University of Pennsylvania; Kyra Williams, University of Pennsylvania*
3. Developing Learning-focused Leaders Through Design-based School Improvement: Lessons Learned Across Germany and the United States (Poster 3). *Corinne Aramburo, University of New Mexico; Elizabeth Zumpe, University of Oklahoma; Nils Reubke, Friedrich Alexander Universität Erlangen Nürnberg*
4. Designing Collaborative Learning Within and Across Districts for Equity-Centered Systems Change (Poster 4). *Alison Fox Resnick, University of Colorado - Boulder; Caitlin Farrell, University of Colorado - Boulder; Kim Boddie Wright, Rice University; Marc L. Stein, Improving Education; Paula Arce-Trigatti, National Network of Education Research-Practice Partnerships; Terrenda Corisa White, University of Colorado - Boulder*
5. Balancing Data and Reflection: Supporting Teachers in Meaningful PDSA Cycles for Equitable Instructional Improvement (Poster 5). *Rachel Ruggirello, Washington University in St. Louis; Alison Brockhouse, Washington University in St. Louis; Gloria Pfeifer, Washington University in St. Louis*
6. When Equity is Not Invoked: Transfer of an Ed.D. Program's Equity Curricula to Generalized Practice (Poster 6). *David Albert Rodes Trautman, University of California - San Diego; Maxwell Yurkofsky, Radford University; Randy W. Hetherington, University of Portland*
7. Tensioning in Continuous Improvement (Poster 7). *Carlos Sandoval, Clemson University; Jonathan R. Dolle, WestEd; Rebecca Colina Neri, Stemuli Studios, Inc.*
8. Teaching Improvement Science in Online Ed.D. Programs: Reducing Geographic Inequities in Leadership Preparation (Poster 8). *Sarah J Zuckerman, University of Nebraska - Lincoln; Daniella Hall Sutherland, University of Vermont*
9. Supporting Local Educational Innovation through Collaborative, Continuous Improvement: Self-Directed/Community-Supported Learning in MOOCs

(Poster 9). *Donald J. Peurach, University of Michigan; Aysha Jerald, University of Michigan; Jacob M. Aguinaga, University of Michigan*

Chairs: *David H. Eddy-Spicer, University of Virginia; Kristen C. Wilcox, University at Albany - SUNY; Elizabeth Zumpe, University of Oklahoma*

Discussant: *Brandi N. Hinnant-Crawford, Clemson University*

20.043. Rethinking Ability and Assessment – From Accommodation to Affirmation. SIG-Inclusion and Accessibility in Educational Assessment; Paper Session InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, K-Town; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Alternative Assessment Evidence: Second Language Development of Deaf and Hard of Hearing Students. *Myeongeun Son, Seoul National University of Science and Technology; Jongwoo Lee, Texas Tech University*
Communication and Language in Multilinguals with Cognitive Disabilities: A Study with Immigrant Mothers and Educators. *Delis Cuellar, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Laurene L. Christensen, Wisconsin Center for Education Research*

Neurodiversity-Affirming Engineering Creativity Assessment: Validating ECAT and Linking ADHD Traits to Creative Productivity. *Zeynep Gonca Akdemir, University of Connecticut; Arash Zaghi, University of Connecticut*

Rethinking Access to Introductory Chemistry in Higher Education: Elevating Neurodivergent Voices. *Leslie Ann Rogers, Montana State University; Jennifer DuBois, Montana State University; Jacqueline Frank, Montana State University; Mosey Hardin, Montana State University; Yu Jiang, Montana State University; Meredith Knowles, Montana State University; Nadezhda Modyanova, Montana State University; Victoria Ng, Montana State University; Marcie Reuer, Montana State University; Molly Schmitt, Montana State University*

Strand-level Impacts of Bundled Accommodations on Literacy Outcomes for Secondary Students with Mild Intellectual Disabilities. *Pei-Ying Lin, University of Saskatchewan*

Discussant: *Shelbi Cole, Student Achievement Partners*

20.044. From Histories to Horizons: Indigenous Language Sovereignty and Artificial Intelligence in Shaping Education's Future. SIG-Indigenous Peoples of the Pacific and Beyond; Paper Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 9; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Kua kī taku puku, ko te waha o raro kei te hiakai tonu. *Hona Black, Massey University; Tomairangi Hipango, Massey University*

Decolonizing Artificial Intelligence: AI and Education from the Perspectives of Indigenous Peoples. *Maung Ting Nyeu,*

University of California - Santa Barbara; Gui Ying Annie Yang-Heim, Illinois State University

Decolonial Voices: Creative resistance, language activism and reclaiming linguistic justice. *Prem Phyak, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Te Reo Māori Pronunciation - Upskilling the Aotearoa NZ Education Workforce through Online and AI Solutions. *Piata Allen, University of Auckland; Jesin James, University of Auckland; Peter Keegan, University of Auckland; Catherine Watson, University of Auckland*

Restoring Mele to the Curriculum: Ka'ohēkani's Impact on Hawaiian Identity in Education. *Kamuella M. Kimokeo, Windward Community College*

Chair: *Teracia Smith, Tamatea Pōkai Whenua (Trust)*

Discussants: *Linda T. Smith, Te Whare Wananga o Awanuiarangi; Kerry Laiana Wong, University of Hawai'i at Manoa*

20.045. Stories of Belonging and Persistence: Latine Students' Connection at HSIs, Relationships and Counter-Narratives. SIG-Latina/o/x Research Issues; Symposium JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum J; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Navigating the 2024 Election: Latine Students Identity, HSI Connection and Persistence Through Video Counter-Storytelling. *Paulette D Garcia Peraza, California State University - Sacramento; Yanira Madrigal-Garcia, California State University - Sacramento; Jenavi De Anda, California State University - Sacramento; Hafsa Omer, California State University - Sacramento; Raven Intal, California State University - Sacramento; Monse Gonzalez, California State University - Sacramento; Savannah Jasmine Espinoza, California State University - Sacramento; Allen Vu, California State University - Sacramento; Ashley Auerbach, Sacramento State University*

Embodying Servingness: The Value of Relationships for Latinx Transfer Students at Hispanic Serving Institutions. *Saskias Casanova, University of California - Santa Cruz; Valeria Jacqueline Alonso Blanco, University of California - Santa Cruz; Citlalli Hernandez, University of California - Santa Cruz; Stefany Miranda Mendoza, University of California - Santa Cruz*

Examining Intersectionality, Resilience, and Sense of Belonging in Latina Students at an HSI. *Dania Cruz-Jimenez, The University of Arizona; Ruth María López, University of Arizona*

Perceptions of the University Environment: Latine/x First-Generation College Students' Family Achievement Guilt and Well-Being. *Monica Aviles-Mercado, California State University - Fresno; Rosa Toro, California State University - Fresno*

Chair: *Yanira Madrigal-Garcia, California State University - Sacramento*

Discussant: *Nancy Acevedo, California State University - San*

Bernardino

20.046. Staying, Leaving, and Thriving: The Complex Realities of Teaching. SIG-Lives of Teachers; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Georgia I; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Exploring the Well-Being of Educators Navigating Restrictive Educational Campaigns. *Jami Carmichael, Arizona State University; Lydia Ross, Arizona State University; Carlos R. Casanova, Arizona State University*

Measuring Colleague Support: Development of a Brief Scale for Teacher Well-Being. *Tim Pressley, Christopher Newport University; David T. Marshall, Auburn University; Heather Walter, George Mason University*

When Experience Walks Away: Why Mid-Career Teachers Leave the Classroom. *Cynthia M. Sistik, National University; Patricia A. Dickenson, National University*

You're Good, I'm Good, We're All Good: Teacher Well-being in an Elementary School During Change. *Jennifer Karnopp, San Diego State University; Peter Bjorklund, University of California - San Diego*

Teachers' Career Advice Networks and Career Decisions: A Mixed-Methods Analysis. *Chunru Dong, University of Maryland; Andrew M. Brantlinger, University of Maryland; Sora Kim, University of Maryland*

Chair: *Kristina M. Valtierra, Colorado College*

Discussant: *Cynthia Arraya Wiltshire, University of Texas - El Paso*

20.047. Ancestral Futures: Sankofa, Afrofuturism, and Black Educational Imagination. SIG-Research Focus on Black Education; Paper Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304B; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Afrofuturism, Dreaming, and Fiction as Praxis for Educational Transformation. *Sosanya M. Jones, Howard University*

Queen Mother Adelaide Sanford: Sankofa Pedagogy and Black Educational Futures. *Lindamichelle Baron, York College - CUNY*

Repairing Harm: Restoring the Spirit of Ubuntu and the Principle of Sankofa. *Shannon Renee Waite, Howard University*

The Sankofa Writing Method and Philadelphia Community Youth Court: A Narrative Framework for Restorative Change. *Ayana T. Hardaway, Stanford University; Francine Hardaway, Philadelphia Community Youth Court*

To the Left: The Makings of a Black Radical Pedagogy. *Noah Nelson, Johns Hopkins University*

Chair: *Khalilah Odessa Ali, Spelman College*

20.048. Motivation, Belonging, and Help-Seeking in Academic Contexts. SIG-Studying and Self-Regulated Learning; Paper

Session

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Los Feliz; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

"Easily Distracted": A Thematic Analysis of College Students' Attentional Self-Efficacy and Self-Regulated Learning. *Bridget K. Daleiden, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Lisa D. Bendixen, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Kendall Hartley, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Abraham Flanigan, Georgia Southern University*

Effort and Interest in Sync? Longitudinal Analysis of Grit in Mathematics. *Tianxue Cui, Dalian Maritime University; Danni Lin, Beijing Normal University; QIMENG LIU, Beijing Normal University*

Fitting In While Being First: Belonging, Help-Seeking, and Social Identity Threat Among First-Generation College Students. *Andrew Holmes Perry, The Ohio State University; Shirley L. Yu, The Ohio State University; Elise C. Allen, University of Northern Colorado; Eric M. Anderman, The Ohio State University; Minjung Kim, The Ohio State University*

I Think I Can (Ask for Help): Analysis of a Self-Efficacy for Academic Help-Seeking Scale. *Jacqueline von Spiegel, The Ohio State University; August Masonheimer, Purdue University; Christopher A. Wolters, The Ohio State University*

Looking Beyond Quantity: A Longitudinal Qualitative Study on How Students Regulate Their Motivation Over Time. *Yeo-eun Kim, Sungkyunkwan University; Wenting Song, Florida State University; Xinyu Liu, Florida State University; Laurel Garrison, Florida State University; Patrick N. Beymer, University of Cincinnati*

Chair: *David B. Miele, Boston College*

Discussant: *Lauren Cabrera, University of Michigan - Dearborn*

20.049. Preparing Future Educators in the Age of AI. SIG-

Technology as an Agent of Change in Teaching and Learning; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Georgia II; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Measuring Preservice Teachers' Efficacy with the Responsible Use of Human-Centered Artificial Intelligence in Education. *Yao Fu, University of Wisconsin - Whitewater; Crystal Machado, Indiana University of Pennsylvania; Jiayi Wang, University of Wisconsin-Stevens Point*

Integrating Generative AI Lesson Planning in Pre-Service Teacher Training: Shifts In Attitudes, Knowledge, and Perception. *Jessica Cai, Northwestern University; Joseph Wong, University of California - Irvine*

Questioning the "Magic" of a Generative Artificial Intelligence Platform with Pre-Service Elementary Teachers. *Jacob Pleasants, University of Oklahoma; Madison Morris, University of Oklahoma*

Discussant: *Itauma Itauma, Northwood University*

Division and SIG Roundtables

20.050. AERA Roundtable Session Wednesday 9:45 am;
Roundtable Session

20.050-1. Artificial Intelligence: Opportunities and Ethical Dilemmas for Student Learning & Systems Change (Table 1). Division A - Administration; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- A Qualitative Multi-District Study of the Integration of AI - Khanmigo. *Dominic Siami Egure, Oklahoma State University; Katherine A. Curry, Oklahoma State University; Jentre J. Olsen, Oklahoma State University; Daniel Hamlin, University of Oklahoma*
- Making Time Count: How Schedulers Approach School Scheduling and the Potential Role of AI. *Amanda Lu, Georgetown Public Policy Institute; Ev Fu Gilbert, Stanford University; Christopher Cleveland, Brown University; Susanna Loeb, Stanford University*
- Navigating and Leading Computer Science and Artificial Intelligence Implementation in Schools. *Imelda Nava-Landeros, University of California - Los Angeles; Marco A. Nava, Los Angeles Unified School District; Justin Betzelberger, University of California - Los Angeles*
- Leadership, Professional Learning, and Collaboration: Examining Enabling Conditions for Teacher AI Engagement in Public Schools. *Xiu Cravens, Vanderbilt University; Xun Zhang, Vanderbilt University*

Chair: *Jie Lin, Shanghai Jiao Tong University*

20.050-2. Building Inclusive Futures: Culturally Competent Leadership and Critical Perspectives for Student Flourishing (Table 2). Division A - Administration; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- Cultivating Culturally Competent Communities of Character: A Transcultural Approach to Educational Leadership Across Differences. *Robert White, ECSU*
- Feedback, Engagement, and Well-being for Student Flourishing. *Jonathan Eckert, Baylor University; Hannah Kapitaniuk, Baylor University; Grant B. Morgan, Baylor University; William L. Sterrett, Baylor University; Marilyn Anderson Rhames, Baylor University*
- MTSS for Social Justice: An ImproveCrit Analysis of a School's Approach to Continuous Improvement. *Rebekah Kang, Loyola Marymount University*
- School-Based Support for Student Mental Health and Wellbeing: From Clarion Call to District Response. *Kristin*

Geiser, John W. Gardner Center for Youth and Their Communities, Stanford University

Chair: *Debalina Maitra, Kennesaw State University*

20.050-3. Revisiting the Past to Reimagine the Future: Liberation, Joy, and Community as Frameworks for Educational Justice and Renewal (Table 3). Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- Centering Resistance and Reimagining Futures Black Women Teachers Navigating No-Excuses Charter Schools. *Brian Collins, Indiana University - Indianapolis*
- Dream Mapping: Worldbuilding cartographies of Black joy in education. *Jacobē Bell, Teachers College, Columbia University*
- "If you think this vilifies the police, then you think police are villains": Teaching Reparations Won as an antidote to copaganda. *Kaitlyn Selman, Illinois State University; Hannah Carson Baggett, Auburn University; Justin Turner, Illinois State University*

The Reality of Restorative Justice: A Critical Ethnography of a Public Elementary School. *Hannah Scott Rohrer-Fitzhugh, Westminster College; Shawn R. Coon, Westminster University*

Chair: *Larry C. Bryant, Metro State University*

20.050-4. Ethnic-Based Organizing and Leadership Development (Table 4). SIG-Asian Americans and Pacific Islanders in Education and Research; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- By and For Hmong Students: Exploring a Youth Conference as Collective Resistance and Educational Transformation. *Chamee Moua, University of California - Davis*
- "Ever Evolving": Filipino American Student Leadership Identity in Ethnic-Based Organizations. *Dominique Orfano Acosta, Claremont University - Pitzer College*
- From anti-racist workers to anti-racist parents: The early evolution of a Filipinx American parent-organized learning collective. *Anna Gail L. Caunca, World Learning*
- "Know history, know self: Nco Ntsoov Peb Haiv Hmoob [Remembering Our Hmong People]" - A Historical Analysis of the Hmong American Student Organization in Higher Education. *Xiong Her, University of California - Los Angeles*

Chair: *Azmi Azam, University of Arizona*

20.050-5. Teacher's Work in Contentious Times: Pedagogy and Teachers' Experiences (Table 5). SIG-Teachers Work/Teacher Unions; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 9:45-

11:15am

Participants:

Learning to Teach Under Fire: Fostering Democratic Classrooms Through Sustaining Black Fugitive Pedagogies. *Neven Matthew Holland, University of California - Los Angeles; Keara L. Williams, University of California - Los Angeles*

Union Teachers of Color's Interpretations of the Silencing of Diversity Discourse in Florida: An Intersectional Qualitative. *Brittany A. Aronson, Pennsylvania State University; Haniyeh Kheirkhah, Pennsylvania State University; Mildred Boveda, Pennsylvania State University; Karla Hernández-Mats, American Federation of Teachers*

The Intensification of Moral Injury in Teachers During the Pandemic. *Denisha Jones, Defending the Early Years; Brianne Kramer, Southern Utah University*

20.050-6. Meaning-making as Social Action across Media, Disciplines, and Identities (Table 6). SIG-Semiotics in Education: Signs, Meanings and Multimodality; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Disrupting Digital Intimacy: A Multimodal Analysis of Gendered Power Dynamics in AI Companionship and Its Educational Implications. *Liang Cao, The Education University of Hong Kong; Qinghua Chen, The Education University of Hong Kong*

Multimodal literacy in secondary language arts classes: High school youths' genre appropriation through multimodal composing. *Hannah Park, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Hongye Zeng, University of Maryland*

Reconceptualizing the "L" in CLIL: English-medium nursing educators' perspectives of translanguaging-trans-semiotizing pedagogy in CLIL collaboration. *Yiqi Liu, The Education University of Hong Kong*

The Semiotics of Stereotypes: Using Memes to unpack Race and Power in Mathematics. *Gregory Benoit, Boston University; Gregory Beaudine, University of Iowa; K. Elizabeth Hammonds, Auburn University; Gabor Salopek, Math Meme Team*

Understanding Learners' Civic Participation via Digital Multimodal Composing: A Systemic Functional Multimodal Discourse Analysis Approach. *Bonnie Xuehua FU, University of Auckland; Lawrence Jun Zhang, University of Auckland*

Chair: *Hengyi Liu, University of Southern Indiana*

20.050-7. Strengthening HĀ (BREATH) in Hawaiian Education: From Pre Service to System Level Leadership (Table 7). SIG-Leadership for School Improvement; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 9:45-

11:15am

Participants:

Strengthening BREATH in Educational Leadership: A Framework for Systemic and Culturally Responsive Change. *Keali'i Kukahiko, University of Hawaii - Manoa*

Teaching Hawaiian Cultural Values and Social Emotional Learning Through Children's Books. *Michele Ebersole, University of Hawaii - Hilo*

Grounding SEL in Nā Hopena A'ō (HĀ): Navigating Tensions in Transforming Policy and Practice. *Margary Martin, University of Hawai'i at Hilo*

Chair: *Margary Martin, University of Hawai'i at Hilo*

20.050-8. The Critical Role of Ethnic Studies in Educational Leadership (Table 8). Division A - Administration; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Reimagining Leadership: When Critical Leadership Praxis Reunites with Ethnic Studies Pedagogy. *Allyson Tintiangco-Cubales, San Francisco State University; Arlene S. Daus-Magbual, San Francisco State University*

Rooted in Ethnic Studies: Designing Professional Development for Educational Leaders. *Tracie Noriega, Association of California School Administrators; Arlene Daus-Magbual, San Francisco State University; Allyson Tintiangco-Cubales, San Francisco State University*

Counterhegemonic Leadership: Addressing the Challenges and Possibilities of Ethnic Studies Implementation for Educational Leaders. *Joaquin Noguera, Loyola Marymount University; Ernesto Colin, Loyola Marymount University; Kenzo K. Sung, Loyola Marymount University; Cynthia M. Alcantar, Loyola Marymount University; Kyo Yamashiro, Loyola Marymount University; William Perez, Loyola Marymount University; Dolores Delgado Bernal, Loyola Marymount University*

Towards Educational Leadership for Justice: Preparing leaders to integrate ethnic studies into their leadership practices. *Yesenia Fernandez, California State University - Dominguez Hills; Kitty M. Fortner, California State University - Dominguez Hills*

Chair: *José Manuel Aguilar-Hernández, California State Polytechnic University - Pomona*

Discussant: *Dolores Delgado Bernal, Loyola Marymount University*

20.051. AERA Roundtable Session Wednesday 9:45 am - Gold 1; Roundtable Session

20.051-1. Roundtable Session 1: Student Learning and Development in College and Beyond (Table 1). Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;

9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- An Ethos of Deserving: Reframing Black Women Collegians' Educational Experiences. *Ekaete Udoh, University of Missouri*
- Hair me out: Unforgetting hairitage and futuring Black feminist possibility. *Quinci Bone't Teer, Cleveland State University; Tristta M. Kuykendall, Cleveland State University*
- Predictors of financial wellness among collegiate women: A revisitiation of demographic and other differences. *Jeremy Wright-Kim, University of Michigan; Michelle C. Garcia, University of Michigan*
- Women and Identity: Longitudinal changes following college. *MaryBeth Walpole, Rowan University; Madeline P. Boehning, Rowan University*

20.051-2. Toward Innovative and Supportive Teaching Practices (Table 2). Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- Institutional Supports of Autonomy, Competence, and Instructional Influence Among Teaching-Focused Faculty. *Meaghan Beth McMurrin, University of California - Riverside; Brian Sato, University of California - Irvine*
- The Perspectives of Culturally Responsive College Instructors in Agriculture Departments at Land Grant Universities. *Aaron Golson, North Carolina A&T State University; Tatiane Russo-Tait, University of Georgia*
- A Latent Class Analysis of Guest Speakers in Undergraduate STEM Courses. *Sara Dozier, California State University - Long Beach; Quentin Sedlacek, Southern Methodist University; Michelle Friend, University of Nebraska - Omaha; Anthony Muro Villa, University of California - Riverside; Maricela Leon, The University of Texas System; Karla Lomeli, Santa Clara University; Greses Perez, Tufts University; Joel Alejandro Mejia, University of Cincinnati*

20.051-3. Teaching for Justice: Centering Identity, Voice, and Real-World Relevance in Diverse Classrooms (Table 3). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- Expanding Multilingual Voices in Social Studies Discussions: One Teacher's Responsive Practice. *Timothy Patterson, Temple University; Lightning Jay, Binghamton University - SUNY; Brian Tauzel, Western Washington University; Ashley Taylor Jaffee, Princeton University; Jenni Conrad, Oregon State University*
- Teachers' Perspectives on the Assets Students Bring to Learning Computational Thinking and Community-Based

Environmental Literacy. *Clare Baek, University of Hawaii - Manoa; Victoria Nguyen, University of California - Irvine; Symone Gyles, University of California - Irvine; Kate Montes-Perales, University of California - Irvine; Mark Warschauer, University of California - Irvine*

Teaching Climate Crisis in the ELA Classroom: A Mixed Method Survey and Interview Study. *Alexandra Panos, University of South Florida; Katharine Hull, University of South Florida; Robert F. Dedrick, University of South Florida; Justo Yanez, University of South Florida - Tampa*

A Case study of a Grade 8 Teacher's Perceptions of Teaching HIV/AIDS in Lebanon. *IHSAN GHAZAL, Boston university*

Enacting Equitable Science Teaching: The Role of Biopsychosocial Histories of Teachers and Learners. *Socorro Herrera, Kansas State University; Jinhua Wang, Kansas State University; Kendra Herrera, Kansas State University*

Chair: *Timothy Patterson, Temple University*

20.051-4. Ethical Mentorship and Transformative Learning: Supporting Preservice Teachers' Growth Through Relational Practice (Table 4). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- Finding Their Footing: A Multi-Case Analysis of Preservice Teachers Navigating Mentor Teacher Relationships. *Christopher Kingsland, Towson University*
- Motivation Regulation Profiles in Preservice Teachers: Implications for Teacher Preparation and Field Practice. *Hyeree Cho, Purdue University*
- Preparing Future Educators for Deeper Learning: Insights from a Qualitative Study on Teacher Candidate Engagement with the Deeper Learning Modules. *Jing Su, University of California - Santa Barbara; Oishee Mujtaba, University of California - Santa Barbara; Matthew D. Bennett, University of California - Santa Barbara; Daniel Rafael Santana, University of California - Santa Barbara; Ying Gao, University of California - Santa Barbara; Yvette Doss, University of California - Santa Barbara; Danielle B. Harlow, University of California - Santa Barbara; Mian Wang, University of California - Santa Barbara*
- Pre-service Teachers' Course Experience and Teaching Commitment relationships: A Latent Profile Analysis. *peili yuan, 北京师范大学; Weiran Wu, Southwest University; nairui yan, South China Normal University; 昱泽陈, Tsinghua University; Huan Song, Beijing Normal University*
- Pre-Service Teachers' Transformative Learning Through Peer Mentoring: A Community of Practice Approach. *Xuexue Yang, SUNY - College at Oneonta*

Chair: *Jing Su, University of California - Santa Barbara*

20.051-5. Workforce Experiences in Early Care and Education

(Table 5). SIG-Early Education and Child Development;
Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Using Quasi-Experimental Evidence to Understand Workforce Experiences in Early Childhood Education and Care. *Samantha Burns, University of Guelph; Elizabeth Dhuey, University of Toronto - Scarborough; Linda White, University of Toronto; Michal Perlman, University of Toronto - OISE*

Centering Teacher Experience: Educator and Director Perspectives on Workforce Needs in Head Start Programs. *Uma Awasthi, University of Missouri; Shinyoung Jeon, University of Missouri; Prabhath Pallewaththa, University of Missouri; Vrushali Gadkari, University of Missouri; Aileen Garcia, University of Missouri*

Risk and Protective Factors for Turnover Intentions Among Early Childhood Educators in Indiana. *Jennifer Finders, Colorado State University; Shawn L. Carlson, Southwest Minnesota State University; Ellen Litkowski, Georgia State University; Megan Purcell, Purdue University*

Urban Early Childhood Providers' Experiences of Compassion Fatigue: A Phenomenological Study. *Jale Aldemir, Coppin State University; Anita Weisburger, Coppin State University; Nicole Anthony, Coppin State University*

The Unseen Struggles: Exploring Work-Related Stress and Coping Strategies Among Early Childhood Teachers. *Seth Badu, New York University; Anthony Woode-Eshun, University of South Florida*

Chair: *Jale Aldemir, Coppin State University*

20.051-6. Voices Across Borders: Identity, Displacement, and the Edge of Belonging (Table 6). SIG-Narrative Research;

Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Morbidity and Mortality: A Narrative Self-Study of two educators' experiences with Higher Educational Trauma. *Eliza A. Pinnegar, Anchorage School District; Mona Beth Zignego, LUMIN Schools*

Re-imaginings Across Borders: Teaching Displaced Children in War Zones. *Simmee Chung, Concordia University - Edmonton*

Understanding Ethnic Minority Students' Multilingual Motivational Selves through Narrative Inquiry. *Kevin Yung, The Education University of Hong Kong*

“What To Do With The Weight Of The World?”: A Hmong American Preservice-Teacher's Visual Narrative. *Sharon Chang, Teachers College, Columbia University; A. Lin Goodwin, Boston College*

Chair: *Theodore Chao, California State University - Fullerton*

20.051-7. Investigating Teacher Development from the Inside Out (Table 7). SIG-Research in Mathematics Education;

Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Cultivating mathematics teacher curiosity. *Jennifer Osuna, Stanford University; Faith Kwon, Stanford University; Miriam Simone Leshin, University of Virginia; Jen Munson, Northwestern University*

Definitions Matter: Preservice Teachers' Conceptions of Antiracist Mathematics Teaching. *Karisma Morton, University of North Texas; Antonieta Barces, University of North Texas; Zutella Holmes, University of North Texas; Queshonda J. Kudaisi, University of North Texas*

Mathematics That Matters for Teaching: Connecting Mathematical and Teaching Practices in a Professional Development Workshop. *Cody Wilson, University of Toronto - OISE*

Rewriting Histories and Futures: Supporting Iterative Goal Setting for Preservice Elementary Mathematics Teacher Development. *Paula Jakopovic, University of Nebraska - Omaha*

The Anti-Exclusionary Mathematics Teacher Identity Development Framework. *Brian Alexander Smith, University of Minnesota - Duluth*

Chair: *Robyn K. Pinilla, University of Texas - El Paso*

20.051-8. Intergenerational Resistance, Agency and Power through Youth Activism (Table 8). SIG-Grassroots

Community and Youth Organizing for Educational Justice;
Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

A Qualitative Exploration of Children's Civic Development in the Context of an Intergenerational Leadership Initiative. *Wendy Y. Perez, NYU Metro Center; Joanna D. Geller, New York University; Lisette DeSouza, NYU Metro Center; Arianna Jackson, Fordham University; Wendy de los Reyes, Claremont University - Claremont McKenna College*

Beyond Liberal Capitalist Pitfalls: Youth Organizers Envision and Enact Participatory Politics. *Wanda Watson, San Jose State University*

Futuring Through Resistance: CARES Dads and the Abolitionist Politics of Black Autonomy in Education. *Denise G. Yull, Binghamton University - SUNY; Marguerite A. Wilson, Binghamton University - SUNY; Chandiren Valayden, Binghamton University - SUNY; Westley Mays, CARES Advocates for families; Thomas Gray, CARES Advocates for families*

Unheard Voices: Reviewing the Literature on Black Parental Resistance in Suburban Schools. *Natasha Folarin Daniels,*

University of Texas at Austin

“You Can’t Ignore Us:” A Phenomenology of Black Student Union Efforts to Rebuild Post-Pandemic. *Celina German, Arizona State University*

Discussant: *Antwan Jefferson, University of Colorado - Denver*

20.052. AERA Roundtable Session Wednesday 9:45 am - Gold 2; Roundtable Session

20.052-1. Advancing Equity in Special and Inclusive Education (Table 1). SIG-Special and Inclusive Education Research; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Toward Equity: Mapping Anti-Racist Methodology in Special Education through A Systematic Review. *Haerin Park, University of Saint Joseph; Yun-Ju Hsiao, Washington State University - Tri-Cities; Benikia Kressler, California State University - Fullerton; Amy K Kunkel, University of Minnesota*

“How Can We Even Be Equitable?”: Building Culturally Responsive Co-Teaching in Shifting Political Contexts. *Brittany Stahlman, University of Minnesota*

Imagining Futures of Support for Alternatively Certified Black Male Special Educators Through Mentoring and PD. *Cametreus Clardy, University of Florida*

Bearing the Burden: Cultural and Psychological Costs for Im/migrant and Refugee Families in Special Education. *Melissa J. Cuba, University of Maine; Adai A. Tefera, University of Arizona*

Chair: *Nisha Acharya Julien, Opportunity Consulting*

20.052-2. Advancing Independence and Communicative Access: Technology and AAC (Table 2). SIG-Special and Inclusive Education Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

EMBRAACE: A Collaborative Framework Empowering Families of Color Navigating Augmentative and Alternative Communication. *Karla Patricia Armendariz, Pennsylvania State University; Lydia L Ocasio-Stoutenburg, Pennsylvania State University*

Intervention Effectiveness of iOS-Based Augmentative and Alternative Communication: A Bayesian Meta-Analysis of Single-Case Experimental Designs. *Yukang Xue, University at Albany - SUNY; Yu Xue, Washington State University; Dongni Guo, University at Albany - SUNY; Gan Jin, Washington State University; Fang Wang, University of South Carolina; Weili Yuan, Washington State University*

Chair: *Jacqueline Lubin, Quinnipiac University*

20.052-3. Beyond Language: Educating for Belonging and Global Citizenship (Table 3). SIG-Critical Educators for Social Justice; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Examining Language Ideologies in Translingual Picture Books. *Saesaem Yoon, University of Washington - Tacoma; Janelle Franco, University of Washington - Tacoma*

More Than Teaching: Educators’ Relational Labor in Newcomer Programs. *Gina Arnone, Research for Action; Dae Y. Kim, Research for Action; Maja Pehrson, Research for Action*

SDGs Integration’s Impact On Chinese College Students’ Cognitive And Action Transformation In English Classrooms. *Yirui Xiang, Shanghai International Studies University*

Chair: *Marc Tohme, New York University*

20.052-4. Decolonial Voices and Educational Futures Across Borders (Table 4). SIG-Critical Educators for Social Justice; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

From Silenced Histories to Empowered Futures: Palestinian Narratives in Israeli Academia. *Rawia Hayik, Sakhnin Academic College for Teacher Education*

Practicing Anticolonial Literacies Against the Settler Literacies of Empire. *Theresa Burruel Stone, Sonoma State University*

Reimagining Refugee Education through Teacher Voice: Post-Migration Ecologies in K12 Schools. *Özge KURU, Turkish Ministry of National Education; Derin Atay, Bahcesehir University*

Learning as Resistance: Afghan Girls Navigating Taliban Education Bans through Underground and Digital Spaces. *Marzhan Ayabekova, University of Massachusetts - Lowell*

Chair: *Rosalie Zdzienicka Fanshel, University of California - Berkeley*

20.052-5. Reclaiming Education as a Humanizing Praxis through Reimagining (Table 5). SIG-Critical Educators for Social Justice; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Do We Dare Disturb the Status Quo?: A Critical Discourse Analysis of CASEL’s Social and Emotional Learning (SEL) Framework. *Adishi Gupta, University of British Columbia; Surita Jhangiani, University of British Columbia; Handel K. Wright, University of British Columbia*

National Survey of Educators Perception of Constitutionality of ‘Don’t Say Gay’ Laws. *Kathryn Watson, Appalachian State University*

Reclaiming Agency and Belonging: Arts-Based Teacher Learning for Diverse, Joyful Classrooms. *Kelly Joann Thelen, Southwest Minnesota State University; Michela Carattini - Mays, Southwest Minnesota State University*

“This Place Can Hold Me”: Educators’ Experiences of Healing in a Wellness-Centered High School. *Shannon McManimon, Viterbo University; Joanna Perez Rizzotto, Milwaukee Public Schools*

Unforgetting Migration: Designing Pedagogies of Belonging for Justice-Oriented Classrooms. *Erica Holyoke, University of Colorado - Denver; Nasir Kaihan, Arizona State University*

20.052-6. Centering Disabled Students in K-12 Education: Reimagining Access, Belonging, and Ways of Knowing (Table 6). SIG-Disability Studies in Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Impacts of Accessible Laboratory Experiences in Chemistry for Blind and Low-Vision Students. *Madeline Haynes, University of Texas at Austin; Lisa Garbrecht, University of Texas at Austin; Yiwen Yang, University of Texas at Austin; Bryan Shaw, Baylor University*

Sensing and World-making with Students with Complex Support Needs. *Srikala Naraian, Teachers College, Columbia University; Maria S. Guarino, Teachers College, Columbia University*

The Crisis of Connection: Being With Students with Severe Disability Labels. *Charna D’Ardenne, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*

Chair: *Mbuh G Payne, Rowan University*

20.052-7. Crippling the Research: Innovative Methodologies of Disability Justice (Table 7). SIG-Disability Studies in Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Beyond Compliance: Disability Justice and Rights-Based Research Ethics in Language Education. *Rosa Dene David, University of British Columbia; Alexandra Ross, University of British Columbia*

Crippling Qualitative Research: Methodological Considerations in Conducting Qualitative Research with Multiply-marginalized Students Disabilities. *Tamara Handy, Teachers College, Columbia University; Adai A. Tefera, University of Arizona*

Crip Wisdoms in Color: Coloring Book as Collaborative Disability Justice Methodology. *Emily Nott, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Miso Kwak, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Enacting Crippling Methodologies: Liberatory Praxis Through

Self-Study in Teacher Education. *Sarah Arvey Tov, University of Washington; Mikaela Zetley, University of California - Los Angeles; David I. Hernandez-Saca, University of Northern Iowa*

Chair: *Casey Woodfield, Rowan University*

20.052-8. Inclusion and Equity in Career and Technical Education and Workplace Learning (Table 8). SIG-Career & Technical Education and Workplace Learning; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Creating “Veteran-Friendly” Workplaces: A Dual Perspective Study. *Diane Gillaspie, Valdosta State University; Jieun You, Valdosta State University*

Gender Roles In the Construction Trades: Barriers and Tools of Resilience as Experienced by Tradeswomen. *Ashley Nesladek, University of Colorado - Denver*

Has the Needle Moved? CTE and Postsecondary Participation of Women in STEM Fields. *Oscar A. Aliaga, University of South Florida; Cindy Matti-lynn Townsend, University of South Florida; Amber D. Dumford, University of South Florida - Tampa*

Reimagining CTE: Trap Feminist Economics and the postwork imagination. *Roya Fathalizadeh, Arizona State University*

Whose Rainbow? An Analysis of Inclusion, Labor, and Futurity in Special Education Work-Based Learning. *Kioshana LaCount Burrell, The Ohio State University; Amber N Johnson, Pennsylvania State University*

Discussant: *Jacob Kirksey, Texas Tech University*

20.053. AERA Roundtable Session Wednesday 9:45 am - Gold 3; Roundtable Session

20.053-1. Innovations in Research Production and Translation: Challenges, Possibilities, and Future Directions (Table 1). SIG-Research Use; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Does AI in Education Research Drive International and Interdisciplinary Collaboration? *Brady Lund, University of North Texas; Zoe Abbie Teel, University of North Texas*

How to reduce practical significance bias in science communication with pre-service teachers? *Kirstin Schmidt, Karlsruhe University of Education; Florian Felix Alfons Kühnwein, Karlsruhe University of Education; Samuel Merk, Karlsruhe University of Education*

Instructor Decision-Making Around Podcasts as Tools for Research Use in Higher Education. *Lindsay E. Persohn, University of South Florida Sarasota-Manatee; Stephanie M Branson, Northern Arizona University; Leah Burger, University of South Florida*

Translational Mindset in STEM: A Structural and Psychometric Examination. *Angela Murray, University of Kansas; Jose Fabian Elizondo-Gonzalez, University of Kansas; Trina E. Emler, University of Kansas*

Chair: *Sarah A. van Ingen Lauer, University of South Florida*

20.053-2. Impact Through Collaboration: Reimagining School Partnerships with Higher Ed and Communities (Table 2). SIG-School, University, Community Collaborative Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Bridging Institutions, Building Intentions: A Cross-Sectional and Exploratory Study of STEM Identity and Career Orientation. *Morgan R. Castillo, Baylor University; Tracey N. Sulak, Baylor University*

Extending the Impact of a STEM Curriculum with a Boundary-Spanning Summer Camp for Middle Schoolers. *Micaha Dean Hughes, North Carolina State University; Aaron Arenas, North Carolina State University; Tameshia Ballard Baldwin, North Carolina State University; LaTricia Townsend, North Carolina State University*

Strengthening School-University-Community Partnerships Within a Teacher Education Service-Learning Course. *Curtis Mason, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Elizabeth Coder, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Cara Gutzmer, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Chair: *Sarah Priscilla Lee, Northwestern University*

20.053-3. Multi-Tiered Support Systems and Targeted Literacy Interventions (Table 3). Division C - Learning and Instruction; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

A Contemporary Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis of the Language Skills of Children with ADHD. *Andrew Eunghyun Chang, Vanderbilt University; Yang Fu, University of Maryland; Jason C. Chow, Vanderbilt University*

Development and Implementation of Tier 1 MTSS for Academic and Behavioral Supports in Elementary Grades. *Minseo Kim, Korea University; Yedana Lee; Seunghyun Son, Korea University; Sungkwan Yang, Konkuk University*

Effectiveness of Enhanced Core Reading Instruction (ECRI) for Student in Tier 2: Years 1-3 Findings. *Elaine Lin Wang, RAND Corporation; John Pane, RAND Corporation; Nancy J. Nelson, Boston University; Marissa Pilger Suhr, University of Washington*

Evaluating a Digital Language Intervention for Grammatical Skills of Linguistically and Socially Diverse First-Graders. *Svenja Wehrhöfer, TU Dortmund University; Fani Lauermann, University of Bonn*

Chair: *Maggie Mnayer, Central Michigan University*

20.053-4. Phonological and Morphological Instruction for Diverse Learners (Table 4). Division C - Learning and Instruction; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Bidirectional Transfer of Phonological Awareness Between Cantonese and English: An Intervention Study. *Yu Wing Chan, Yew Chung College of Early Childhood Education*
Morphological Instruction for Diverse Secondary Learners: A Systematic Review of Evidence and Equity Implications. *Jamie Alain Smith Levitan, University of Maryland*
Perceptual Identification of English Consonant Contrasts under Phonetic Positions and Acoustic Conditions. *Katherine Jiawen Ren, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Chuang Wang, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Christine Leong, University of Nottingham*
Rethinking Reading Development through the Gut-Brain Axis. *Danielle Marie Rylak, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*
The Development of Phonological Awareness in Early Literacy: A Multilevel Modeling Analysis. *Xiaohan Wang, University of Toronto; Songtao Wang, University of Toronto - OISE; Kathleen Hlpfner-Boucher, University of Toronto - OISE; Becky Chen, University of Toronto - OISE*

Chair: *Anne Blackstock-Bernstein, University of California - Los Angeles*

20.053-5. Supporting Positive Mathematical Affect Through Instruction and Informal Learning (Table 5). Division C - Learning and Instruction; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Effects of Active Breaks on Mathematics Anxiety: A Multisite RCT. *Valeria Di Martino, University of Palermo; Rosa Bellacicco, University of Turin; Clarissa Sorrentino, University of Salento*
From Belief to Intention: Why Math Students May Not Make Plans to Learn from Mistakes. *Jerry Nelluvelil, Harvard University; Jon R. Star, Harvard University*
Supports for De-tracked Mathematics Instruction: Seventh Grade Students' Descriptions of "Good at Math". *Jennifer L. Ruef, University of Oregon; J. Chris Willingham, James Madison University; Zoë Constantine, University of Oregon*
The Effects of Creating Versus Experiencing Math Walks Stops in Informal Learning Settings. *Candace A. Walkington, Southern Methodist University; Anthony J. Petrosino, Southern Methodist University; Jennifer D. Sayed, Southern Methodist University; Saki L. Milton, Southern Methodist University; Safia Khan, Southern Methodist University; Eric Desjardins, Southern Methodist University; Theodora Beauchamp, Southern Methodist University; Mary Cabanas,*

Southern Methodist University; Elizabeth Stringer, Southern Methodist University

Chair: *Madeleine Kingan, Harvard University*

20.053-6. Pathways to Purpose: Examining Youth Engagement in Informal Education Environments (Table 6). SIG- Informal Learning Environment Research; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Adapting Collaboration: Examining Adolescent Communication in Unstructured STEM Learning Environments. *Danielle Pascual Espino, Pepperdine University; Julia Savoca Gibson, American University; Nastassia N. Jones, Southern University - Baton Rouge; Anna Wilson, Southern University - Baton Rouge; Seung B. Lee, Pepperdine University; Eric R. Hamilton, Pepperdine University*

Rasquache Storytelling: Collaborative Learning Through Arts and Advocacy in a Los Angeles Youth Program. *Jackson Gzehoviak, University of California - Los Angeles; Caroline Kanner, Clockshop; Christopher Jadallah, University of California - Los Angeles*

The Impact of Informal STEM Learning Experiences on High School Students' STEM Career Intentions. *Yun Zhou, Shanghai Jiao Tong University; Chuntao Leng, Shanghai Jiao Tong University; Feng-Kuang Chiang, Shanghai Jiao Tong University*

Youth Perceptions of Climate Change and its Impact on Conservation Education. *Tess Gavrielle Levinson, Wildlife Conservation Society; Su-Jen Roberts, Wildlife Conservation Society*

20.053-7. Giftedness, Creativity, and Talent Roundtable: Instrumentation and Identification (Table 7). SIG- Research on Giftedness, Creativity and Talent; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Influence of Semantic Distance and Psycholinguistic Characteristics on Remote Associates Test Performance Under Time Constraints. *Vicky Weiqing Ji, University of North Texas; Selcuk Acar, University of North Texas; Peyton Perduyn, University of North Texas*

Validating the Achievement Orientation Model in Gifted Underachievers: A Bayesian Structural Equation Modeling Approach. *Brendha Christie Tanujaya, Purdue University; Michel Cordoba, Purdue University; Nielsen Pereira, Purdue University/Gifted Education Research & Resource Institute*

Enhancing Gifted Student Identification: Applying Differential Item Functioning in Validating the HOPE Teacher Rating

Scale. *Shahnaz Safitri, Purdue University; Brendha Christie Tanujaya, Purdue University; Nielsen Pereira, Purdue University/Gifted Education Research & Resource Institute*

Factor Structure and Measurement Invariance of the Imaginative Capability Scale Across Sex. *Lindsay Ellis Lee, Advanced Learning Research & Consulting, LLC; Kristen N. Lamb, University of Alabama*

Enhancing Gifted Identification: A Machine Learning Analysis of the HOPE Teacher Rating Scale Responses. *Hyeseong Lee, Lewis University; Jake Cho, Lewis University; Anne Marie Walsh, Plainfield North High School*

Chair: *Kimberley L. Chandler, Johns Hopkins University*

20.053-8. Novel Mixed Methods Research Applications: Insights into the Diversity of Mixed Methods Research (Table 8). SIG-Mixed Methods Research; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Using Multiple Regression with Mixed Data as a Pragmatic Exploratory Approach to Theorizing. *Evan McClintock, University of Colorado - Denver*

Map Faculty and Staff Well-Being with Mixed Methods. *Nichole Fehrenbach, Johns Hopkins University*

Charting Thematic and Global Trends in TESOL Mixed Methods Research: Integrating Computational Modeling and Bibliometrics. *Naseh Shahri, San Diego State University; Ismaeil Fazel, Medical University of South Carolina*

Mapping Methodological Integration in Mixed Methods Health Intervention Studies with Economic Evaluations: A Systematic Review. *Yealiza Khaleque Kheya, University of Cincinnati*

Chair: *Kelly Ann Peña, Rutgers University*

Division and SIG Posters

20.054. AERA Poster Session Wednesday 9:45am; Poster Session

20.054-1. Diverse Learners and Inclusive Teaching Practices. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Poster Session Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 9:45-11:15am

Posters:

1. Adding Pedagogical Agents Who Point or Trace to Children's Instructional Videos (Poster 1). *Meixia Cheng, Central China Normal University; Fuxing Wang, Central China Normal University; Xiaoxue Leng, Central China Normal University*
2. A Novel Approach to Pupillometry and Learner Engagement Without Eye-Tracking Devices (Poster 2). *Jiaju Huang, University of Toronto - OISE; Earl Woodruff, University of*

- Toronto - OISE; Milan Lasic, University of Toronto - OISE*
3. Between Margins and Machines: Agency and Digital Literacy in Rural-Urban Migrant Children's Digital Use (Poster 3). *Ziwen Mei, University of British Columbia; Guofang Li, University of British Columbia*
 4. Beyond Bans: Factors Influencing Teachers' Social Media Selection for Language Teaching and Its Implications for TPACK in Restrictive Contexts (Poster 4). *Aisel Akhmedova, Michigan State University*
 5. Color me confounded: A critical analysis of media comparisons on ChatGPT in education (Poster 5). *Alyssa Lawson, Colby College; Amédee Marchand Martella, University of Georgia; Joshua Weidlich, University of Zurich; Miriam Mulders, University of Duisburg-Essen; Josef Buchner, St. Gallen University of Teacher Education*
 6. Creating Change for Equitable Opportunities, Improved Learning, and Sustainability through Innovative Technology-enriched Learning Community Development (Poster 6). *Leslie A. Williams, University of Oklahoma; Linda Atkinson, University of Oklahoma; Danny Mattox, University of Oklahoma; Sharon G. Dean, University of Oklahoma*
 7. Emotional Design for Learning in Virtual Reality: Effects of Object Luminosity, Lighting, and Action (Poster 7). *Yuli Shao, New York University; Yuqi Hang, New York University; Xinyue Jiao, New York University; Bruce D. Homer, Graduate Center - CUNY; Jan L. Plass, New York University*
 8. Exploring the influences of immersive stimuli in virtual reality-based teacher training simulations (Poster 8). *Alex Barrett, Florida State University*
 9. Latent Transitions in Cooperative, Competitive, and Individualistic Attitudes in an Inquiry-based Online Learning Context (Poster 9). *Eun Hye Ham, Kongju National University; You-kyung Lee, Sookmyung Women's University; Yoonsun Shin, Sookmyung Women's University*
 10. Learning Gains from Online Math Practice at Varying Difficulty Levels: Prior Achievement Matters (Poster 10). *Erjing Zhang, University of California - Los Angeles; Xiaozhu An, IXL Learning; Mary Hargis, IXL Learning; Christina C Schonberg, IXL Learning; Bozhidar M. Bashkov, IXL Learning*

20.054-2. Division H Poster Session. Division H - Research, Evaluation and Assessment in Schools; Poster Session Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 9:45-11:15am

Posters:

11. Evaluation of a Translanguaging in Science Professional Development Project: Focusing on Institutional Support (Poster 11). *Hien Thi Tran, University of Houston; Jie Zhang, University of Houston; Zhenjie Hou, University of Houston; May JadAllah, Independent Researcher in Amman, JORDAN; Sissy S. Wong, University of Houston; Haemin*

Kim, University of Houston; Araceli Enriquez-Andrade, University of Houston; Samuel Katende, University of Houston; Yonglin Ruan, University of Houston

12. State-Led Student-Centered Learning in Context: A Comparative Case Study Approach (Poster 12). *Kelly Organ, FullScale; Jilliam N. Joe, Aurora Institute*

20.054-3. AERA Division K Section 6 In-Service Educators - Poster Session 1. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Poster Session Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 9:45-11:15am

Posters:

13. Beyond Disruption: Creating a Model to Identify and Support Educator Professional Learning and Implementation Needs (Poster 13). *Jenna Nelson, Concordia University - Chicago; Hank Bohanon, Loyola University Chicago*
14. Improving Content and Pedagogical Knowledge and Self-Efficacy via In-Service Teacher Training in Rural Uganda (Poster 14). *Jai Bum Koo, Florida State University*
15. Online Professional Learning: Reconceptualizing Teacher Outcomes, Connecting to Student Reading Growth (Poster 15). *Mary Bratsch-Hines, University of Florida; Stephanie Snidarich, University of Florida; Julianna Banks, University of Florida; Rui Xu, University of Florida; Erin Mowry, University of Florida; Tyran Butler, University of Florida*
16. Building an Equity-Focused Elementary CS Endorsement Program: Lessons Learned from the Piloting Year (Poster 16). *Ruohan Liu, Seattle University; Charisse Cowan Pitre, Seattle University; Imani Sims, Seattle University; Preston Hervey, Seattle Country Day School*
17. How Formation Modes Shape Organizational Culture: Evidence From Four International TVET Teacher Innovation Teams (Poster 17). *xiaochen tong, East China Normal University*
18. Hybrid Communities in Virtual Maker-centered Professional Development: Teacher Participation and Community Formation (Poster 18). *Mengying Jiang, Utah State University; Kristin A. Searle, Utah State University*
19. Integration of Virtual Cognitive Coaching with Learning by Scientific Design: A Framework for Enhanced Teacher Professional Development (Poster 19). *Dawn Thieman, University of Missouri - St. Louis; Natalie Bolton, University of Missouri - St. Louis*
20. Learning Takes Two: The Effects of Colleague and Leader Presence in a Professional-learning MOOC for Rural Teachers (Poster 20). *Zhong Sun, Capital Normal University; Chin-Hsi Lin, University of Hong Kong; Shuang Li, Capital Normal University; Shuo Han, Capital Normal University; Zicong Song, The University of Hong Kong; Keyi Zhou, University of Hong Kong*
21. Listening to Pre-K and K Teachers in a Suburban School: (Re)imagining Support for Children Experiencing Homelessness (Poster 21). *Jinhee Kim, Kennesaw State*

University; Jihye Kim, Kennesaw State University; Arvin Johnson, Kennesaw State University

22. Reimagining Agricultural Education: Teacher Beliefs and Intentions to Apply Social Science Research Concepts (Poster 22). *Erin Gorter, California Polytechnic State University - San Luis Obispo; Hannah C. Parker, California Polytechnic State University - San Luis Obispo; Nicole Ray, Cal Poly, San Luis Obispo*
23. Supervisor support and teachers' knowledge sharing behaviors: Mediation of needs satisfaction and moderation of trust (Poster 23). *Yanmin Cao, Shijazhuang Engineering Vocational College; Yonghong Cai, Beijing Normal University; Runjia Tang, Capital Normal University; Lu Zhou, Chongqing University; Qianjin Li, Nanjing Normal University; Xiaoming Peng, Nanjing Normal University*
24. Tracing Teacher Perception Shifts of Scientific Uncertainty: A Longitudinal Study Across Two-year Practice-based Professional Development (Poster 24). *Yiwen Li, Arizona State University; Ying-Chih Chen, Arizona State University; Michelle Jordan, Arizona State University; Carlos Meza-Torres, Arizona State University; Jongchan Park, Arizona State University; Yu Ye, Arizona State University*
25. Understanding In-Service Teachers' Learning: Longitudinal Patterns of Knowledge Sharing in an Online Professional Learning Community (Poster 25). *Jo-Chi Hsiao, National Yang Ming Chiao Tung University; Shan-Mei Chang, Tsinghua University; Han-Yu Chi, National Chengchi University of Taiwan; Ler-Ui Lin, National Tsing Hua University of Taiwan*
26. We DO Talk About Science in Elementary School (Poster 26). *Kearstie Hernandez, Los Angeles Unified School District*
27. What Are We Doing Successfully? What Is Lacking? Stakeholders' Experiences from Diverse Teacher Communities (Poster 27). *Denisse Maribel Hinojosa, Texas Tech University; Robert Luera Urrutia, Texas Tech University*

20.054-4. Division L Section 6 Social Policy, Inequality, and Student Outcomes: Poster Session. Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Poster Session Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 9:45-11:15am

Posters:

28. Does Receiving an IEP Improve Attendance Outcomes? (Poster 28). *Samantha Kreda Peters, University of Pennsylvania; Michael A. Gottfried, University of Pennsylvania*
29. Do Private Preschools Advance Child Development in China? Dosage, Quality, and Heterogeneous Effects (Poster 29). *QIFAN Zhang, University of California - Berkeley; Bruce Fuller, University of California - Berkeley*
30. Migration, Education, and Labor Market Participation: Analyzing Economic Activity Types Across Age and

Gender in Colombia (Poster 30). *Ari Jiayu An, Stanford University*

31. Special Education Categorization Varies Across the Distribution of Student Family Income (Poster 31). *Nicholas James Ainsworth, University of California - Irvine; Christopher Cleveland, Brown University; Leah Clark, U.S. Census Bureau; Jacob Hibbel, University of California - Davis; Quentin Brummet, Michigan State University; Andrew Saultz, Pacific University Oregon; Emily K. Penner, University of California - Irvine; Michelle Spiegel, Stanford University; Paul Y. Yoo, University of California - Irvine; Juan Camilo Cristancho, University of California - Irvine; Paul Hanselman, University of California - Irvine; Andrew Penner, University of California - Irvine*
32. The New Normal: A Cohort Analysis of How COVID-19 Disruptions Altered English Language Proficiency in California (Poster 32). *Marlene Saint Martin, University of California - Los Angeles*
33. Uncovering Themes and Trends of Achievement Gap Research Literature: A Natural Language Processing Approach (Poster 33). *Huang Wu, University of Missouri - Kansas City*

20.054-5. In the Room or Down the Hall? Rethinking Occupational Therapy Access and Instructional Alignment. SIG-Action Research; Poster Session Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 9:45-11:15am

Poster:

34. In the Room or Down the Hall? Rethinking Occupational Therapy Access and Instructional Alignment (Poster 34). *Isabella Durso, Pace University; Francine C. Falk-Ross, Pace University*

20.054-6. Educating for Democracy: A Preliminary Exploration of Civic Education and Funding. SIG-Democratic Citizenship in Education; Poster Session Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 9:45-11:15am

Poster:

35. Educating for Democracy: A Preliminary Exploration of Civic Education and Funding (Poster 35). *Mallory Lineberger, University of Texas at Austin; Elizabeth Aritonang, UT Austin*

20.054-7. Instructional Technology SIG Poster Presentations. SIG-Instructional Technology; Poster Session Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 9:45-11:15am

Posters:

36. AutoLit: Enhancing Human-AI Collaboration in Systematic Literature Reviews Through Interactive LLM Support (Poster 36). *Xiaojiao Sun, University of South Florida; Bo Pei, University of South Florida; Zhaowei Zhang, University*

- of South Florida
37. Developing Prompt Engineering Competence Framework: Comparing China, EU, and U.S. Educators' Digital Literacy Standards (Poster 37). *Wei Wang, University of Tennessee; Wen Yi Hu, Anhui Normal University; Jialu Zhao, Stanford University; Qi Sun, University at Albany - SUNY; Zhongxin Zheng, The George Washington University; Yuexin Duan, University of Tennessee*
 38. Feedback-Driven Strategic Shifts in Immersive Virtual Reality Training: A Multi-Phase Behavioral-Mining Study (Poster 38). *Idowu David Awoyemi, University of Alabama; Jewoong Moon, University of Alabama; Stephen Emmanuel Abu, University of Alabama; Raissa Marchiori, Florida Gulf Coast University; Siyuan Song, Arizona State University*
 39. Generative AI Agent Persona Effects on Pre-service Teachers' Pedagogical Response Strategies in 3D Teacher Simulation (Poster 39). *Jieun Lim, Daegu National University of Education; Yunseo Lee, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Gyuri Byun, Seoul National University; Yeil Jeong, Seoul National University; Unggi Lee, Korea University*
 40. How Novices Learn to Code With AI: Analyzing the Structure and Effects of Error-Type-Specific Feedback in LLM-Based Tutors (Poster 40). *Cheolil Lim, Seoul National University; Eunseo Lee, Seoul National University; Eunsang Eom, Team monolith*
 41. How Trust, Anxiety, and Self-Efficacy Shape International Students Generative AI Dependency (Poster 41). *Nilloufar Bayati, North Carolina State University; Florence Martin, North Carolina State University*
 42. K-12 Teachers' Needs, Experiences, and Attitudes with AI use in Education: Evidence from Facebook Discussions (Poster 42). *Joanne Ma, Rutgers University; Dake Zhang, Rutgers University*
 43. Mapping the Dimensions of AI Literacy Self-Efficacy Among Middle Schoolers: An Exploratory Factor Analysis (Poster 43). *Bridget Newell, University of Florida; Xiaoman Wang, Western Michigan University; Albert Dieter Ritzhaupt, University of Florida; Anthony Botelho, University of Florida; Christine Wusylko, Kennesaw State University; Priyadarshini Ganapathy Prasad, University of Florida; Loraine Cisternas-Garcia, University of Florida; Angela M. Kohnen, University of Florida; Kevin Cen, University of Florida*
 44. Modeling Behavioral Dynamics and Cognitive States in VR Safety Training: A Learning Analytics Approach (Poster 44). *Stephen Emmanuel Abu, University of Alabama; Jewoong Moon, University of Alabama; Idowu David Awoyemi, University of Alabama; Raissa Marchiori, Florida Gulf Coast University; Siyuan Song, Arizona State University*
 45. Online Interactive Educational Products: Implications on Student Outcomes? (Poster 45). *Joseph E. Miller, Ascend Learning; Kari Hodge, Ascend Learning*
 46. Preparing to Teach with Games: Exploring ICT Strategy Exposure and DGBL Perceptions (Poster 46). *Nezaket Sema Gündoğdu, Middle East Technical University; Nur Cakir, Middle East Technical University; Evrim Baran, Iowa State University*
 47. Promoting Higher Order Thinking Through Reflection with a Generative AI Chatbot (Poster 47). *Banu Karyagdi, University of California - Irvine; Hongyang Zhao, University of California - Irvine; Shuyuan Yu, University of California - Irvine; Ella Rose, University of California - Irvine; Shayan Doroudi, University of California - Irvine; Katherine T Rhodes, University of California - Irvine; Lindsey E. Richland, University of California - Irvine*
 48. Unlocking Future Women STEM Workforce: Cultivating Girls' Interests in Computing, AI, and Cybersecurity (Poster 48). *Mahnaz Moallem, Towson University; Folashade Agbolade, Towson University*
 49. Using Affordance Analysis to Strategize the Integration of AI-Generated Instructor Avatars within MOOCs (Poster 49). *Rebecca M. Quintana, University of Michigan; Annie Zhou, University of Michigan*
- 20.054-8. A Deep Dive into War Metaphors Describing Impostor Phenomenon.** SIG-Language and Social Processes; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 9:45-11:15am
Poster:
50. "Fighting an Uphill Battle": A Deep Dive into War Metaphors Describing Impostor Phenomenon (Poster 50). *Devasmita Chakraverty, Indian Institute of Management*
- 20.054-9. Higher Education.** SIG-Philosophical Studies in Education; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 9:45-11:15am
Posters:
51. Accompaniment: An Ethical Approach for Collaboration in Higher Education (Poster 51). *Cara Elizabeth Furman, Hunter College - CUNY; Phoebe Gilpin, Hunter College - CUNY; Siri Ranganath, Rutgers University - New Brunswick*
52. Machines, Memory, and Inverted Utopians: Value Creation in Doctoral Education (Poster 52). *Jessica Heybach, Western Michigan University; Austin J. Pickup, Aurora University*
53. Thick Concepts and Their Ethical Boundaries in Educational Research (Poster 53). *Stephen Sowa, University of Southampton; Chris Brown, University of Southampton*
54. What's in a feeling? Shame and Expression on University Campuses (Poster 54). *Penelope Lusk, University of Pennsylvania*
Chair: *Jason Cong Lin, The Education University of Hong Kong*
- 20.054-10. Exploring Teacher and Leader Well-Being.** SIG-Stress, Coping, and Resilience; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall -

Exhibit Hall A; 9:45-11:15am

Posters:

55. Beyond Survival: Fostering Teacher Wellbeing and Agency Through the Legacies of Educational Resistance (Poster 55). *Farshad Ghasemi, University of Missouri*
56. A narrative research synthesis of principal well-being from 1978 to 2024 (Poster 56). *Junjun Chen, Education University of Hong Kong; Wendan XU, The Education University of Hong Kong; Cheng Jin, The Education University of Hong Kong*
57. Understanding Teacher Well-Being Through the Lens of the Job Demands-Resources Model (Poster 57). *Yingxiu Li, The Education University of Hong Kong; Junjun Chen, Education University of Hong Kong; Junying Lu, The Education University of Hong Kong; Xiang Wang, Hong Kong Baptist University*

20.054-11. Division D - Section 1 Poster Session. Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Poster Session Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 9:45-11:15am

Poster:

58. Diagnosing Spatial and Executive Skills in XR Vocational Training With Cognitive Diagnosis (Poster 58). *Sae Hyun Park, New York University; Sangbeak Ye, Florida Atlantic University; Ayse Torres, Florida Atlantic University*

20.055. e-Lightning Ed-Talk Session 2 - Stage 1. AERA e-Lightning Ed-Talks; AERA Ed Talk Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Exhibit Hall A - Stage 1; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- A Novel Approach to Pupillometry and Learner Engagement Without Eye-Tracking Devices (Stage 1, 9:50 AM). *Jiaju Huang, University of Toronto - OISE; Earl Woodruff, University of Toronto - OISE; Milan Lazic, University of Toronto - OISE*
- Emotional Design for Learning in Virtual Reality: Effects of Object Luminosity, Lighting, and Action (Stage 1, 9:59 AM). *Yuli Shao, New York University; Yuqi Hang, New York University; Xinyue Jiao, New York University; Bruce D. Homer, Graduate Center - CUNY; Jan L. Plass, New York University*
- Learning Gains from Online Math Practice at Varying Difficulty Levels: Prior Achievement Matters (Stage 1, 10:08 AM). *Erjing Zhang, University of California - Los Angeles; Xiaozhu An, IXL Learning; Mary Hargis, IXL Learning; Christina C Schonberg, IXL Learning; Bozhidar M. Bashkov, IXL Learning*
- Understanding In-Service Teachers' Learning: Longitudinal Patterns of Knowledge Sharing in an Online Professional Learning Community (Stage 1, 10:17 AM). *Jo-Chi Hsiao, National Yang Ming Chiao Tung University; Shan-Mei Chang, Tsinghua University; Han-Yu Chi, National*

Chengchi University of Taiwan; Ler-Ui Lin, National Tsing Hua University of Taiwan

We DO Talk About Science in Elementary School (Stage 1, 10:26 AM). *Kearstie Hernandez, Los Angeles Unified School District*

What Are We Doing Successfully? What Is Lacking? Stakeholders' Experiences from Diverse Teacher Communities (Stage 1, 10:35 AM). *Denisse Maribel Hinojosa, Texas Tech University; Robert Luera Urrutia, Texas Tech University*

Does Receiving an IEP Improve Attendance Outcomes? (Stage 1, 10:44 AM). *Samantha Kreda Peters, University of Pennsylvania; Michael A. Gottfried, University of Pennsylvania*

Do Private Preschools Advance Child Development in China? Dosage, Quality, and Heterogeneous Effects (Stage 1, 10:53 AM). *QIFAN Zhang, University of California - Berkeley; Bruce Fuller, University of California - Berkeley*

Special Education Categorization Varies Across the Distribution of Student Family Income (Stage 1, 11:02 AM). *Nicholas James Ainsworth, University of California - Irvine; Christopher Cleveland, Brown University; Leah Clark, U.S. Census Bureau; Jacob Hibel, University of California - Davis; Quentin Brummet, Michigan State University; Andrew Saultz, Pacific University Oregon; Emily K. Penner, University of California - Irvine; Michelle Spiegel, Stanford University; Paul Y. Yoo, University of California - Irvine; Juan Camilo Cristancho, University of California - Irvine; Paul Hanselman, University of California - Irvine; Andrew Penner, University of California - Irvine*

Chair: *Rand Quinn, University of Pennsylvania*

20.056. e-Lightning Ed-Talk Session 2 - Stage 2. AERA e-Lightning Ed-Talks; AERA Ed Talk Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Exhibit Hall A - Stage 2; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- Educating for Democracy: A Preliminary Exploration of Civic Education and Funding (Stage 2, 9:50 AM). *Mallory Lineberger, University of Texas at Austin; Elizabeth Aritonang, UT Austin*
- AutoLit: Enhancing Human-AI Collaboration in Systematic Literature Reviews Through Interactive LLM Support (Stage 2, 9:59 AM). *Xiaojiao Sun, University of South Florida; Bo Pei, University of South Florida; Zhaowei Zhang, University of South Florida*
- Developing Prompt Engineering Competence Framework: Comparing China, EU, and U.S. Educators' Digital Literacy Standards (Stage 2, 10:08 AM). *Wei Wang, University of Tennessee; Wen Yi Hu, AnHui Normal University; Jialu Zhao, Stanford University; Qi Sun, University at Albany - SUNY; Zhongxin Zheng, The George Washington University; Yuexin Duan, University of Tennessee*
- Feedback-Driven Strategic Shifts in Immersive Virtual Reality

Training: A Multi-Phase Behavioral-Mining Study (Stage 2, 10:17 AM). *Idowu David Awoyemi, University of Alabama; Jewoong Moon, University of Alabama; Stephen Emmanuel Abu, University of Alabama; Raissa Marchiori, Florida Gulf Coast University; Siyuan Song, Arizona State University*

How Trust, Anxiety, and Self-Efficacy Shape International Students Generative AI Dependency (Stage 2, 10:26 AM). *Nilloufar Bayati, North Carolina State University; Florence Martin, North Carolina State University*

Promoting Higher Order Thinking Through Reflection with a Generative AI Chatbot (Stage 2, 10:35 AM). *Banu Karyagdi, University of California - Irvine; Hongyang Zhao, University of California - Irvine; Shuyuan Yu, University of California - Irvine; Ella Rose, University of California - Irvine; Shayan Doroudi, University of California - Irvine; Katherine T Rhodes, University of California - Irvine; Lindsey E. Richland, University of California - Irvine*

Unlocking Future Women STEM Workforce: Cultivating Girls' Interests in Computing, AI, and Cybersecurity (Stage 2, 10:44 AM). *Mahnaz Moallem, Towson University; Folashade Agbolade, Towson University*

Using Affordance Analysis to Strategize the Integration of AI-Generated Instructor Avatars within MOOCs (Stage 2, 10:53 AM). *Rebecca M. Quintana, University of Michigan; Annie Zhou, University of Michigan*

Accompaniment: An Ethical Approach for Collaboration in Higher Education (Stage 2, 11:02 AM). *Cara Elizabeth Furman, Hunter College - CUNY; Phoebe Gilpin, Hunter College - CUNY; Siri Ranganath, Rutgers University - New Brunswick*

Chair: *Chrystalla Mouza, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Wednesday, April 8th, 10:15 am

Governance Meetings and Events

21.001. AERA Council Meeting: Closed Meeting. AERA Governance; Governance Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 518;
10:15am to 1:15pm
Chair: *Maisha T. Winn, Stanford University*

Wednesday, April 8th, 11:45 am

Presidential Sessions

22.010. Crit Moving: Black, Brown, and Queer Coalitions for Liberated Educational Futures. AERA Presidential Session; Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 404AB;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Chair: *Omi Salas-SantaCruz, University of Utah*

Participants: *Tiffani Marie, San Jose State University; Kenjus T. Watson, American University; Tracy Lachica Buenavista, California State University - Northridge; Edward R. Curammeng, California State University - Dominguez Hills; Ed Brockenbrough, University of Pennsylvania; Nichole M. Garcia, Rutgers University; Noor Ali, Northeastern University*

Discussant: *Daniel Gilbert Solorzano, University of California - Los Angeles*

22.011. Designing Transformative Research for Systemic Change in Teaching and Learning. AERA Presidential Session; Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Chair: *Na'ilah Suad Nasir, Spencer Foundation*

Participants: *Linda Darling-Hammond, Learning Policy Institute; Emma D. Hipolito, University of California - Los Angeles; Cheryl C. Holcomb-McCoy, American University*

Discussant: *Hirokazu Yoshikawa, New York University*

22.012. Unforgetting Histories, Shaping Futures: AAPI Studies in K-12 Classrooms. AERA Presidential Session; Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 409AB;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Chair: *Noreen Naseem Rodriguez, Michigan State University*

Discussants: *Jennifer Higgs, University of California - Davis; Sohyun An, Kennesaw State University*

Panelists: *Esther June Kim, College of William & Mary; Michael Brown, University of Michigan; Virginia Nguyen, Portola High School, Irvine; Danny Diaz, University of California - Los Angeles*

Committee Sessions

22.013. A Future Advancing Gender Equity. Committee on Scholars and Advocates for Gender Equity in Education;
Paper Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 511C;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Exploring Future Thinking Under Academic Gender Stereotype

Congruency: A Dual-Task Experiment in China. 詹景欣,
Beijing Normal University

“I did it anyway”: Subjugated Feminist Knowledges and
Affective Futures of Girls’ Education in India. *Namrata
Namrata, Arizona State University*

Imagining Educational Futures without Gender-based Violence:
Remedy and Repair for/through Student Peer Educators.
Jason Laker, San José State University

Youth Rights, Marriage, Education Access, and Health: A
Global Analysis of Legal Protections and Policy Gaps.
*Prattama Santoso Utomo, University of Rochester; Jialin
Yan, University of Rochester*

**22.014. Division A Fireside Chat: Navigating Political Contexts
in PK–12 Education: Research-Informed Strategies for
Public Education.** Graduate Student Council Cosponsored
with Division A - Administration; Invited Speaker Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 402A;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Chair: *Jennifer Banegas, Pepperdine University*

Discussant: *Benjamin Lebovitz, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Panelists: *Michelle D. Young, University of California - Berkeley;
Clemens Avalos, United Teachers Los Angeles; Scott
Schmerelson, Los Angeles Unified School District; Marisa
Saunders, University of California*

Division Sessions

**22.015. Collective Organizing and Scholarship for Social
Justice.** Division B - Curriculum Studies; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304A;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Collective Inquiry and Action Toward Educational Justice in
Hawai‘i Public Schools. *Lois A. Yamauchi, University of
Hawai‘i at Manoa; Colleen Rost-Banik, University of
Hawai‘i at Manoa; E. Brook Chapman de Sousa, University
of Hawai‘i at Mānoa; Waynele Emi Yu, University of
Hawai‘i at Mānoa*

Coalition building with unions: Learning to influence policy
and legislation. *Ruchi Agarwal-Rangnath, University of San
Francisco; Margarita I. Berta-Avila, California State
University - Sacramento*

(Counter)Insurgency in the Entangled History of Racial
Capitalism, Colonialism, and Fascism. *Jairo I. Fúñez-
Flores, Independent Researcher*

When Formal Education Lags Behind Struggle: Student
Activism, Global Justice, and the Praxis of Paradigm Shifts.
*Rouhollah Aghasaleh, California State Polytechnic
University - Humboldt*

Abolitionist Futures: Building Solidarity and Power through
Labor Organizing. *Erica R. Meiners, Northeastern Illinois
University; Therese M. Quinn, University of Illinois at*

Chicago

Chair: *Kevin Kumashiro, Independent Consultant*

Discussant: *William C. Ayers, University of Illinois at Chicago*

**22.016. Can Education Stop Killer Robots? Exploring Values,
Ethics, and Impacts in K12 Computer Science
Instruction.** Division C - Learning and Instruction;
Structured Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 515A;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

1. AI and the Arts: Critical Insights from Stand-Up Comedy
and Creative Practic (Poster 1). *Sepehr Vakil, Northwestern
University; William Paik, Northwestern University; Samir
Abdul, Independent Scholar; Mike Knight, Independent
Scholar*
2. “So Yeah, No, It’s Not Ethical”: How Young People
Contemplate the Ethics of GenAI (Poster 2). *Charles Logan,
Northwestern University; Sepehr Vakil, Northwestern
University*
3. Towards Social Conscious CS: Incorporating Equity,
Technoskepticism, and Technoethics in CSed Standards
(Poster 3). *Marie K. Heath, Loyola University Maryland*
4. Vibe Coding, Gatekeeping, and Learning to Program with
ChatGPT (Poster 4). *Max Shafer-Landau, University of
Wisconsin - Madison; Matthew Berland, University of
Wisconsin - Madison; Daniel P. Moore, Seton Hall
University; Antero Garcia, Stanford University; Nicole
Mirra, University of California - Los Angeles*
5. Bits, Bytes & Better Judgment: A Digital Humanities Lens
on Teacher Education and Ethical K-12 Computing (Poster
5). *Anthony Wheeler, Graduate Center - CUNY*
6. Critical Computing Co-design: Developing and
implementing lessons with K-12 computing teachers to
integrate critical perspectives (Poster 6). *Anne Drew Hu,
Michigan State University*
7. Teens’ Ethical Considerations When Building babyGPTs
(Poster 7). *Luis Morales-Navarro, University of
Pennsylvania; Daniel J Noh, University of Pennsylvania;
Yasmin B. Kafai, University of Pennsylvania*
8. K-12 Student Agency in Addressing Ethics and Impacts of
Computing: A Review of the Literature (Poster 8). *Brooke
Starks, Michigan State University; Hyein Jee, Michigan
State University; Xinyue Zhou, Michigan State University;
Michael L. Lachney, Michigan State University; Rafi Santo,
Telos Learning LLC; Jean J. Ryoo, University of California -
Los Angeles*
9. A Systematic Literature Review of Ethical Frameworks in
Computer Science for K-12 and Higher Education (Poster
9). *Hyein Jee, Michigan State University; Brooke Starks,
Michigan State University; Xinyue Zhou, Michigan State
University; Michael L. Lachney, Michigan State University;
Rafi Santo, Telos Learning LLC; Jean J. Ryoo, University of
California - Los Angeles*

10. Computing Impacts and Ethics in the New CSTA Standards Draft: A Synthesis of Expert Perspectives (Poster 10). *David Phelps, Telos Learning LLC; Jean J. Ryoo, University of California - Los Angeles; Rafi Santo, Telos Learning LLC; Michael L. Lachney, Michigan State University*
11. Seeds of Connection: An Indigenous Knowledge Approach to Interrogate Computing and Computing Education (Poster 11). *Cherise McBride, Stanford University; Clifford H. Lee, Northeastern University*
12. “Re-membering” in CS: A Multi-case Study of Distributed Support for Ethically Aware Computing Education (Poster 12). *Madison C Allen Kuyenga, Pennsylvania State University*

Chairs: *Rafi Santo, Telos Learning LLC; Jean J. Ryoo, University of California - Los Angeles; Michael L. Lachney, Michigan State University*

Discussant: *Thomas M. Philip, University of California - Berkeley*

22.017. Community-Informed STEM Learning. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Working Group Roundtable Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 501A; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Strengthening Pre-Service Elementary Science Education with Community Storytelling. *Ari Hock, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

Tracing Purpose(s) in Practice: A case study of community-centered grassroots engineering in northern Tanzania. *Maximilian Sherard, University of North Texas; Jessie Zarazaga, Southern Methodist University*

Designing Meaningful Computing Education for Diaspora Youth. *Yeshi Paljor, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

Contextualizing Institutional Data with Lived Experience: Collaborative mapping to catalyze data science learning and engagement. *Heather Killen, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

How STEM Learning Impacts Indigenous Students’ Use of Community in Self-Identification. *Victor Begay, Cascadia College*

Chair: *Heather Killen, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

22.018. Imagining the Future(s) of Close Reading. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Symposium Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Los Feliz; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

The Structure of Close Reading. *Johanna Winant, Reed College*

Pen and Paper Play: Countering ChatGPT with 20th Century Close Reading and Writing Practices. *Scott Jarvie, San Jose State University; Michael Lockett, Michigan State University*

Close Reading After Distraction: Attentional Discipline and the Futures of Interpretation. *Robert Jean LeBlanc, University of Lethbridge; T. Philip Nichols, Baylor University*

Chair: *Robert Jean LeBlanc, University of Lethbridge*

Discussant: *Carol D. Lee, Northwestern University*

22.019. Mindsets and Motivation Across Contexts: Developmental and Disciplinary Perspectives on Self-Beliefs and Learning. Division C - Learning and Instruction Cosponsored with SIG-Motivation in Education; Paper Session Westin Bonaventure, Level 2, Mt. Washington; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Interconnectivity for the Island Ridge Curve: A Demonstration with Growth Mindset and Self-Concept in Reading. *Yuyang Cai, Shanghai International Studies University; Qianwen Ge, Shanghai International Studies University*

Longitudinal Associations Between Achievement Goals and Cooperative and Competitive Attitudes: Random-Intercept Cross-Lagged Panel Model. *You-kyung Lee, Sookmyung Women's University; Eunjin Seo, Texas State University; Yoonsun Shin, Sookmyung Women's University*

Navigating Failure: A Mixed-Methods Study on Doctoral Students’ Failure Mindsets, Research Development, and Well-Being Outcomes. *Faming Wang, Zhejiang University; Yanjin Shi, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Ronnel B. King, Chinese University of Hong Kong*

“Not Smart Enough”: STEM Mindsets and the Impostor Phenomenon in Adolescents. *Kahyun Lee, University of Houston; Joung Yon Choi, University of Houston; Allison Master, University of Houston*

Understanding Motivation-Mindsets in English Learning: The Roles of Basic Psychological Needs, Language Learning Anxiety, and English Proficiency. *Jiatong Zhang, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Barry Bai, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Hongfang Li, Baicaooyuan Kindergarten; Yu Su, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Qingyao Dan, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; To Chan, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Miranda Lin, Illinois State University*

Chair: *Eunjin Seo, Texas State University*

Discussant: *Katherine M. Muenks, University of Texas at Austin*

22.020. Positioning Youth as Organic Intellectuals to Address Belonging Blindspots that Get Overlooked in Contemporary Educational Research. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Workshop Westin Bonaventure, Level 3, Santa Monica D; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Chairs: *Joanna N. Ali, North Carolina State University; Briana Green, Michigan State University; DeLeon Gray, North Carolina State University*

Discussant: *Janeen Perry-Campbell, Wake County Public School System*

22.021. Teaching and Pre-Service Teacher Learning in Mathematics. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Paper Session

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Santa Barbara C;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Examining Mathematics-Rich Discussions in Face-to-Face and Online Teacher Education Settings. *Yue Tang, Pennsylvania State University; Cory Tondreau, Pennsylvania State University; Rachel Miriam Vriend Croninger, Pennsylvania State University; Sara E. Baszczewski, Pennsylvania State University; Emilee A. Herman, Pennsylvania State University; Gwendolyn Lloyd, Pennsylvania State University; P. Karen Murphy, Pennsylvania State University*

Exploring Characteristics of Horizon Content Knowledge of Prospective Secondary Mathematics Teachers. *Xiaoying CHEN, China West Normal University; Bomi Shin, Chonnam National University*

Preservice Elementary Teachers' Mathematical Reasoning in Small-Group Discussions: Comparing Two Modalities of Quality Talk Intervention. *P. Karen Murphy, Pennsylvania State University; Gwendolyn Lloyd, Pennsylvania State University; Emilee A. Herman, Pennsylvania State University; Rachel Miriam Vriend Croninger, Pennsylvania State University; Yue Tang, Pennsylvania State University; Cory Tondreau, Pennsylvania State University; Sara E. Baszczewski, Pennsylvania State University*

Scaling Dialogic Teaching: How Group Size Shapes Tutor Talk Moves in Virtual Tutoring. *Amirpasha Zandieh, University of Colorado - Boulder*

Chair: *Darolyn A. Flaggs, Kennesaw State University*

Discussant: *Weichen Zhao, San Diego State University*

22.022. Developing and Validating Tools for Student Learning and Experience. Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Paper Session

InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Wilshire Grand Ballroom II; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Developing a survey to measure university instructors' attitudes toward student feedback. *Merry Chailis, Singapore University of Social Sciences; Feng Lin, Singapore University of Social Sciences*

Development of an Assessment Framework and Measurement Tool for College Students' Creativity. *Yawen Cheng, Peking University; Xiaoting Huang, Peking University*

Investigating the MI Student Voice Perception Survey in a Population of Cognitively Impaired Students. *Gavin Vance, Kent School District; Davie Store, Kent ISD; Jennifer Rotach, Kent ISD; Daeja Marzette, Kent Intermediate School District*

Student Postsecondary Culture Survey: Psychometric Evaluation for Equitable Postsecondary Readiness Measurement. *Rachel S. Martin, OneGoal; Gina G. Romano, Ivy Tech Community College*

Diagnosing Struggles in CS/DS Education: Learning Analytics and Educational Data Mining for Data-Driven Instruction

and Assessment. *Jungwon Kyung, University of Massachusetts - Amherst; Steven James Moore, Carnegie Mellon University; Seungjoo Kim, Carnegie Mellon University*

22.023. Invited Panel Division D Equity & Inclusion

Committee: When Knowledge Is Under Attack: Science, Evidence, and DEI in an Age of Backlash. Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Invited Speaker Session

InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, K-Town; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Chair: *Steven M. Sanders, Oregon State University*

Panelists: *Adam Voight, Cleveland State University; Michele Lee, Northern Arizona University; Regina J. Giraldo-Garcia, Ball State University; Marketa Burnett, University of Connecticut; Anne M. Galletta, Cleveland State University*

22.024. Reorienting Method: Counter-Story, Embodiment, and Refusal as Currency in Qualitative Inquiry. Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Paper Session

InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 6th Floor, Metropolitan; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

A (Hopeful) Theory of Everything: Counter-storytelling with Chela Sandoval and Ernst Bloch. *Daniel Thalkar, University of San Diego*

Dancing Themselves Free: A Qualitative Study Examining Black Girls' Embodied Literacies in Majorette Dance Spaces. *Tempestt S. Johnson, University of South Carolina*

Echoes Without Sanctuary: A Black Queer Feminist Methodology of Grief. *Ashley Williams, University of Georgia*

Challenging Dominant Paradigms: Culturally Relevant Research Methods. *Michelle Parkins, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Chair: *Daniel Thalkar, University of San Diego*

22.025. Towards Equitable Access to Mental Health Services in School: Teamwork Across Interdisciplinary Scholars and Professionals. Division E - Counseling and Human Development; Symposium

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 301B; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

"This is Real": A Thematic Analysis of Parent Perspectives on School Mental Health Services. *Alexandra Allen, Boston University; Courtney Newman, University of Virginia; Jennifer Greif Green, Boston University*

Centering Equity and Educational Justice: Exploring Implementation Challenges within Multi-tiered Systems of Support for Reading. *Ayana Bass, Boston University*

The State of Research on Culturally Responsive Social-Emotional Learning: A Systematic Review of the Literature.

Ruchi Mendiratta Khanna, Boston University; Manuel Angel Ramirez, Boston University; Jennifer Greif Green, Boston University

Beyond the Canvas: A Mixed Methods SEL-Arts Program Study. *Samantha Paris Hutchinson, University of California - Santa Barbara*

Examining Latino Families Language Access and Participation in their Children's IEP Meetings, ¿Qué está pasando? *Manuel Angel Ramirez, Boston University; Zach Rossetti, Boston University; Lola Argiro, Boston University*

Youth as Co-Designers: Critiquing Mental Health Surveys from the Ground Up. *Jean Pauline Serrano, University of California - Santa Barbara; Jill D. Sharkey, University of California - Santa Barbara*

Chairs: *Alexandra Allen, Boston University; Jennifer Greif Green, Boston University*

Discussant: *Shane R. Jimerson, University of California - Santa Barbara*

22.026. Remembering the Legacy of Racial, Economic, and Geographical Injustices in the Pursuit of Educational Justice and Renewal. Division G - Social Context of Education; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 303B;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Mapping Inequity: Critical Geography and Advanced Course Access in Urban School Contexts. *Eudarius Jones, University of Memphis; Charisse A. Gulosino, University of Memphis*

Slavery's Lingering Effects on Racial Inequality in Southern School Enrollment. *Karen Phelan Kozlowski, University of Southern Mississippi; Matthew Ward, University of Southern Mississippi*

Social and Emotional Labor of Concentrated Debt: Youth Experiences of Public Transportation in Baltimore City. *Kristy Theodore, Johns Hopkins University; Norma Day-Vines, Johns Hopkins University; Richard Lofton, Johns Hopkins University*

"This history...it's just so difficult...": Pre-Service Teachers Consider Teaching About the Racial Violence of Lynching. *Brian C. Gibbs, Georgia College & State University*

Chair: *Linn E. Posey-Maddox, Temple University*

22.027. Research-Practice Partnerships for Educational Equity: Sustaining Good Work in Challenging Times. Division G - Social Context of Education; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 301A;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Reimagining Indigenous Research Partnerships Through Sovereignty and Reciprocity. *Kate Morman, Northwestern University; Cong Wang, Northwestern University; Priscilla Diaz-Gonzalez, Princeton University; Kelly House,*

Northwestern University; J. Solomon Milner, Northwestern University; Stephanie Fryberg, Northwestern University
Practitioner Perspectives: Embedding Research Frameworks in School Processes. *Perla Rodriguez, Beaverton School District; Veronica Galvan, Beaverton School District; Sho Shigeoka, Beaverton School District; Toshiko Maurizio, Beaverton School District*

The Wellness Center: Forging Equity in Medical and Academic Systems. *Emily Srisarajivakul, University of Memphis; Angela Hargrave, University of Memphis; Marissa Gray, University of Memphis; Meredith Embree, University of Memphis*

Chair: *Kate Morman, Northwestern University*

Discussant: *Stephanie Fryberg, Northwestern University*

22.028. Unapologetically Leading: Black Women Shaping the Future of Education. Division G - Social Context of Education; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 303A;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Lessons in Leadership: What My Grandmother and Othermothers Taught Me. *Marcelle M. Haddix, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Guided by a Goddess, Not Managed by a Maid: Strategies for Black Women Leaders in Navigating Misogynoir and Achieving Success. *Tambra O. Jackson, Indiana University - Indianapolis*

Beyond Survival: Reclaiming Power and Purpose in Black Women's Educational Leadership. *Denise M. Taliaferro Baszile, Wayne State University*

Voices at the Intersections: Black Women's Educational Leadership and Social Contexts. *Monika Williams Shealey, Temple University*

Chair: *Ayana Allen-Handy, Hofstra University*

Discussant: *Ayanna F. Brown, Erikson Institute*

22.029. Ethics and Guidelines for AI-Assisted Assessment Across Professions. Division I - Education in the Professions; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum J;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

AI, Automation Bias, and Social Accountability in Medical Education. *Jane Lindsay Miller, University of Iowa*

Human vs. Artificial Intelligence (AI) Inferencing: The Comparison of AI and Simulated Participant (SP) Based Inferencing and Ethical Implications. *Amelia Wallace, Old Dominion University*

Guidelines for Generative AI in Engineering Design Teaching and Learning. *Justin L. Hess, Purdue University*

Hallucination vs Interpretation: Rethinking Accuracy and Precision in AI-Assisted Data Extraction for Knowledge Synthesis. *Xi Long, University of Illinois at Chicago; Christy*

K. Boscardin, University of California - San Francisco; Lauren Maggio, University of Illinois at Chicago; Joseph Costello, University of Illinois at Chicago; Yoon Soo Park, University of Illinois at Chicago; Ralph Gonzales, University of California - San Francisco; Rasmayah Hammoudeh, University of California - San Francisco; Ki Lai, University of California - San Francisco; Brian Christopher Gin, University of Illinois at Chicago

Chairs: *Kuan Xing, University of Iowa; Brian Christopher Gin, University of Illinois at Chicago*

Discussants: *Jane Lindsay Miller, University of Iowa; Christine Park, University of Illinois at Chicago*

22.030. Mentoring and belonging in student educational journeys. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum G; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

BUILDing STEM Futures: The Role of Undergraduate Research and Mentorship in Developing Graduate Degree Aspirations. *Kevin Eagan, University of California - Los Angeles; Shuhan Ai, University of California - Los Angeles*

Developing Community College Students' Scholarly Habitus through Intentional Mentor/Femtorng Practices. *Danielle Huddlestun, San Diego State University; Marissa Vasquez, San Diego State University; Cassandra Aaron, University of North Texas*

First-Generation Chicana/Latina Experiences in Undergraduate Research Mentorship. *Mariana Carrola, UC Davis*

Fostering a Sense of Belonging among Transfers: A Peer-Mentoring Program at a Four-Year Institution. *Yu April Chen, Louisiana State University; Jingwen Liu, Louisiana State University; Doyinsola Esther Ogunremi, Louisiana State University; Madalyn McGinnis, Louisiana State University*

Discussant: *Mayra Marquez-Mendez, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*

22.031. Reframing College Access: Student Agency, Readiness, and the Politics of Preparation. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum F; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

From Applicants to Bridge-Builders: Reframing Student Roles in College Access. *Stephanie Luna-Lopez, University of California - Davis*

AVID Insights: Diverse Paths to College Predisposition and Search. *Brian Holzman, Texas A&M University; Aminah Crawford, Texas A&M University; Kristian Edosomwan, University of Houston*

Figuring the Ideal College Student: How Early College High School Replicates Hierarchy. *Julia C. Duncheon, University*

of Washington; Daniel Yi, University of Washington
Problematising Common College-readiness Strategies: Learning from the Past to Benefit High School Students' Futures. *Katrina K. Morrison, University of Delaware; Marcia Gail Headley, University of Delaware; Henry May, University of Delaware; Jeffrey Robert Klein, University of Delaware; Roderick L. Carey, University of Delaware*

Chair: *J. Audra Williams, Arizona State University*

Discussant: *Michael Lanford, University of North Georgia*

22.032. Sunny Days or Stormy Skies? Navigating Mentorship, Leadership, and Workplace Climate in Higher Education. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum H; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Paradoxical Leadership: The Small Wins and Big Victories of Interim Academic Administrators. *Jay R. Dee, University of Massachusetts - Boston; Anne M. DeFelippo, Salem State University; Cheryl Daly, Kittery and Marshwood School Districts*

Stellar Guidance: Exploring the Dynamics of Postdoctoral Mentoring in Scientific Collaborative Communities of Practice. *Lois Calian Trautvetter, Northwestern University; Brenda L. Anderson, Northwestern University*

Co-creating with Colegas: Examining Staff's Perception of Workplace Climate at a Texas HSI Community College. *Monica Hernandez, University of Texas - San Antonio; Claudia Garcia-Louis, The University of Texas San Antonio; Eric Luis Uriegas, University of Texas - San Antonio*

Chair: *Ashley N. Gaskew, Baruch College - CUNY*

Discussant: *Jude Paul Matias Dizon, California State University - East Bay*

22.033. Complexities in Preservice Science Teacher Learning and Practice. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 8; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Mixed Messages: What Elementary Preservice Teachers Learn About Science Teaching from their Cooperating Teachers. *Meredith Vaughn, San Diego State University; Donna L. Ross, San Diego State University; Jenna Porter, California State University - Sacramento; Corinne Lardy, California State University - Sacramento; Hui-Ju Huang, California State University - Sacramento*

Organizational Structures and Mental Models Enabling Preservice Teachers' Culturally Relevant Science Teaching: A Conceptual Framework. *Britney L. Jones, Fairfield University; Fiona Brady, Fairfield University; Joanna Dalton, Fairfield University*

Preservice Teachers Perspectives on Contextualized, Language

Literacy-Rich, Inquiry-Centered Science Instruction. *Maria Alexandra Walsh, University of Houston; Sissy S. Wong, University of Houston; Hien Thi Tran, University of Houston; Jie Zhang, University of Houston; Laveria Hutchison, University of Houston; Elisa M. Holcomb, University of Houston; Samuel Katende, University of Houston*

Tensions in Science Planning and Teaching: Insights from an Elementary Teacher Education Program. *Felisha Dake, Colorado State University- Pueblo*

Building Preservice Teachers' Self-Efficacy for Teaching with Online Digital Technologies in Mathematics and Science. *Maria L. Fernandez, Florida International University*

Chair: *Sophie Rebecca Korn Gallagher, Los Angeles County Office of Education*

Discussant: *Roxanne Greitz Miller, Chapman University*

22.034. Language, Power, Belonging: Decolonizing Support in Schools. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 2; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Critical Theory, Culturally Relevant Pedagogy, and the Issue with English-Only Assessments. *Rebekah Lea Phelps, Texas Tech University; Jocelyn Belden, Georgia State University*

Decolonizing Social-Emotional Learning (SEL): Teachers' SEL Practices to Cultivate Minoritized Afghan Students' Diasporic Citizenship in Multilingual/Multicultural ELD Classrooms. *Hannah Kim, University of Colorado - Boulder*

Equity and Institutional Change in Teacher Education Programs: Organizational Implications from Multilingual Teacher Candidates. *Tuba Angay-Crowder, Kennesaw State University; Jayoung Choi, Kennesaw State University; Zurisaray Espinosa, Kennesaw State University; Brianna Arias, Kennesaw State University*

Shifting Teachers' Beliefs and Practices to Support Multilingual Learners with Disabilities. *Suheyta Sarisahin, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Gloria A. Carcoba Falomir, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Alain Bengochea, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Tracy Spies, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*

Chair: *Kara Mitchell Viesca, University of Nebraska - Lincoln*

Discussant: *Kara Mitchell Viesca, University of Nebraska - Lincoln*

22.035. Networked Justice: Identity, Community, & Radical Possibility in Teacher Professional Learning. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 9; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Black Women Science Teachers Strive Toward Self-Definition Through a Draw a Science Teacher Activity. *Alexis Riley,*

New York University

Dialogic Feminist Gatherings: Teacher Training Action For Equality And Violence Prevention in Special Education. *Sara Carbonell, University of Valencia; Esther Roca Campos, University of Valencia; Garazi Lopez de Aguilera, University of Barcelona; Miguel Ángel Pulido, Ramón Llull University; Alfonso Rodríguez-Oramas, Instituto Natura (Mexico); Guillermo Legorburo-Torres, University Rovira i Virgili*

The 'schooling' of Ethnic Studies and possibilities for community-grounded teacher praxis. *Ian Slattery, University of California - Santa Cruz*

Who Connects and How: Collaboration Network Structures Among Indigenous Teachers Across Efficacy, Co-Production, and Urban-Rural Contexts. *Hstao-Chi Juan, National Taichung University of Education; Yi-Hwa Liou, National Taipei University of Education*

Chair: *Zachary A. Casey, Rhodes College*

Discussant: *Audrey Lucero, University of Oregon*

22.036. Reconfiguring teacher learning as joy and connection: Longitudinal pathways for collaboration in justice-centered science instruction. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Symposium

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 6; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

"Not let [social justice] go": Ideological homecoming in PLC learning and elementary science justice-centered teaching. *Cristina M. Betancourt, University of Wisconsin - Eau Claire; Manka M. Varghese, University of Washington*

Cultivating Teachers' Social Justice-Forward Adaptive Expertise Through Generative Professional Learning Spaces. *Kerry Soo Von Esch, Seattle University; Hsin-Jung Li, University of Washington; Matt Stewart, University of Washington; Sarah Jaewon Lee, University of Washington*

Studios of Joy: Co-Designing for Expansive Teacher and Student Learning. *Sarah Jaewon Lee, University of Washington; Jessica J. Thompson, University of Washington*

Centering family knowledge: Teacher-developed home-school connections pedagogies in the elementary science classroom. *Grace Cornell Gonzales, University of Washington; Jessica J. Thompson, University of Washington; Sarah Jaewon Lee, University of Washington*

Chair: *Jessica J. Thompson, University of Washington*

Discussant: *Leema G. Berland, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

22.037. The Possibilities are Endless: AI in Teacher Educator Development. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 1; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

A Collective Self-Study of Teacher Educators on Preparing Teachers for Reflective AI-Integrated Pedagogy. *Sehyun Yun, Ball State University; Hyeonho Henry Yu, Ball State University; Younkung Hong, Ball State University*

GenAI-Induced Emotions and Creativity in Teacher Educators' Informal and Incidental Learning for Instructional Design. *Yinyin Zhou, Xi'an Jiaotong-Liverpool University; Qian Wang, Xi'an Jiaotong-Liverpool University*

Generative AI in Teacher Education: Exploring Pre-Service and Educator Perspectives and Practices. *Siv M. Gamlem, Volda University College; Samantha-Kaye Johnston, University of Melbourne; Synnøve Moltudal, Volda University College; Joshua McGrane, University of Melbourne; Therese N. Hopfenbeck, University of Melbourne*

Learning Journeys of Teacher Educators who participated in a novel AI Literacy Professional Learning program. *Rebecca R. Deutscher, Stanford University; Victor R. Lee, Stanford University; Tammy Wu Moriarty, Stanford University; Christine Bywater, Stanford University; Jessica Ann, Stanford University*

Chair: *Shalaunda M. Reeves, University of Tennessee*
 Discussant: *Keith E. Howard, Chapman University*

22.038. We Gon' Be Alright: Teaching, Healing, and Resisting with Black Youth. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session
 JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 7; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Healing Through Teaching: Black Women Educators Cultivating Giftedness with Culture and Care. *Sydney Carroll, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Brittany Nicole Anderson, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Ginaya Littlejohn, University of North Carolina - Charlotte*

Ignoring Ibrahim: Teaching Black Boys with Refugee Backgrounds in the School/Prison Nexus. *Maeve Wall, California State University - Northridge*

“Say It in English”: Examining Raciolinguistic Ideologies in Rural K–8 Science Classrooms. *Stephanie Tracey, Clemson University*

The Amplifying of Black Girls’ Voices: Applying Culturally Relevant Pedagogy and BlackCrit to Challenge STEM Bias. *Uchenna Emenaha Miles, University of Texas - San Antonio; Raketa Ouedraogo-Thomas, University of North Carolina - Charlotte*

Cultivating a Black Ethos: Designing for Justice, Solidarity, and Educational Transformation. *Davena Y. Jackson, Boston University; Ashley Houston-King, Boston University*

Chair: *Taryn T.C. Brown, University of Florida*
 Discussant: *Danielle Charlemagne, University of Georgia*

22.039. Culture Wars in the Classroom: From Book Bans to DEI Rollbacks. Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 10; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Mama Bears in the Belly of the Beast: Moms for Liberty’s Far-Right Organizing in a Progressive State. *Danfeng Soto-Vigil Koon, University of San Francisco; Huriya Jabbar, University of Southern California; Kiah Combs, University of San Francisco; Mira McDavitt, University of San Francisco; Tamra Malone, University of San Francisco; Teresa Leyva, University of San Francisco*

Erasing Diversity: Demographic Shifts, Segregation and the Rise of Book Bans in U.S. Schools. *Erica Frankenberg, Pennsylvania State University; Caprial E. Farrington, University of Georgia; Sarah McCollum, University of Georgia; Genevieve P. Siegel-Hawley, Virginia Commonwealth University; Talia S. Leibovitz, University of California - Berkeley; Elizabeth H. DeBray, University of Georgia; Janelle T. Scott, University of California - Berkeley; Kathryn A. McDermott, University of Massachusetts - Amherst; Caprial E. Farrington, University of Georgia*

Institutional Adaptation and the Rollback of LGBTQIA+ Supports Under Texas SB 17. *Sherri Castillo, Austin Community College; Randy Lopez, University of Texas at Austin; Keren Esmeralda Gomez, University of Texas at Austin*

Rolling Back “Anti-Racism,” Defending “Diversity:” How One Suburban District Navigated the DEI Backlash. *Nadirah Farah Foley, Washington University in St. Louis*

Chair: *Jenna Doane, The University of New Mexico*
 Discussant: *Jennifer Ventimiglia, Northeastern Illinois University*

SIG Sessions

22.040. Artist Salons as Sites of Unforgetting: Reimagining Liberatory-Education through Plays, Film, Poetry, Novella, and Collage. SIG-Arts-Based Educational Research; Demonstration/Performance
 Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 309; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Black Girls Shine. *Jessica Reed, Michigan State University*

Collaging Black and Indigenous Education Sovereignties. *Anna Almore, University of Michigan*

Poetry in Motion: A Black Feminist Inquiry in Sound and Story. *Autumn A. Griffin, University of North Carolina - Charlotte*

Maya Political Memory: Patrullero Voices Disrupting Civil War Narratives Through Collaborative Cinema. *Alex Mejia, San Francisco State University*

Sonic Memories and Sonic Storytelling as Methodology: Multimodal Literacies & Mixtape Composing with Transnational Girls of Color. *Jordyn Alyse Simmons,*

University of Houston; Tairan Qiu, Stanford University
Black Girl Art: Refusal and Reimagining Through Arts-Based
Research. *Jazmen Moore, Stony Brook University - SUNY*
Chairs: *monét cooper, University of Michigan; Renée Wilmot,*
Michigan State University
Discussant: *Ruth Nicole Brown, Michigan State University*

22.041. Del Son al Corazón: Afro-Indigenous Music, Fandango Pedagogy, and Community-Based Transformative Justice. SIG-Critical Educators for Social Justice; Workshop
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304C;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participant:

Del Son al Corazón: Afro-Indigenous Music, Fandango
Pedagogy, and Community-Based Transformative Justice.
Yared Portillo, University of California - Berkeley; Rosalilia
Martinez Mendoza, Stanford University; Cueponcaxochitl D.
Moreno Sandoval, California State University - Stanislaus;
Gustavo Garcia, University of New Mexico

Chair: *Natalia Maria Toscano, University of New Mexico*

22.042. Building Bridges and Breaking Barriers in Early Education Pedagogical Practice and Family-School Partnerships. SIG-Early Education and Child Development; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Georgia I;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Children's Classroom Engagement as Predictor of Primary
Caregiver-Teacher Communication Quality in Urban Head
Start Classrooms. *Sophia Betar, Tufts University; Christine*
M. McWayne, Tufts University

“Las matemáticas siempre van conmigo de la mano”: Latine
Caregivers' Math Values, Attitudes, and Beliefs. *Paola*
Montufar Soria, New York University; Genesis Reyes, New
York University; Gigliana Melzi, New York University

Elevating Latine Families Through Co-Design to Support Early
STEM Education. *Daniel Garcia, University of California -*
Irvine; Vanessa Noemy Bermudez, University of California -
Irvine; Wendy Giovanna Gomez, Santa Ana Early Learning
Initiative; Alejandra Gallegos, Santa Ana Early Learning
Initiative; Sophia Betar, Tufts University; Karla Carino,
Tufts University; Lupe Gomez, Santa Ana Unified School
District; Cynthia Parker, Tufts University; Keely Orlando,
Santa Ana Unified School District; Christine M. McWayne,
Tufts University; Andres Sebastian Bustamante, University
of California - Irvine

How Communication Moderates Parents' Barriers to School
Engagement and Satisfaction with School Contact and
Support. *Karla Carino, Tufts University; Christine M.*
McWayne, Tufts University

Health Routines as a Bridge Between Family Bonding and
STEM Learning. *Diana Marie Romano, University of*
California - Irvine; Daniel Garcia, University of California -

Irvine; Maria Jose Anderson-Coto, UC Irvine; Wendy
Giovanna Gomez, Santa Ana Early Learning Initiative;
Alejandra Gallegos, Santa Ana Early Learning Initiative;
Laura Hernandez, University of California - Irvine; Eric
Dearing, Boston College; Eduardo Bustamante, University
of Illinois at Chicago; June Ahn, University of California -
Irvine; Andres Sebastian Bustamante, University of
California - Irvine

Chair: *Daniel Garcia, University of California - Irvine*

Discussant: *Eric Dearing, Boston College*

22.043. Nature-connectedness and the More-than-human in Environmental Education - Environmental Education SIG Structured Poster Session. SIG-Environmental
Education; Structured Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 515B;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

1. Child-nature connectedness in an outdoor preschool
program (Poster 1). *Stacey Alfonso, University of*
Washington
2. "Natureness" in popular children's literature: Implications
for early development and environmental connection (Poster
2). *Emily Small, University of Washington; Stacey Alfonso,*
University of Washington; Gail E. Joseph, University of
Washington; Emily Holm Tobin, University of Washington
3. Nurturing complementary nature-culture relations through
routine field-based learning with people, places, and more-
than-humans (Poster 3). *Jordan D. Sherry-Wagner,*
University of Washington - Bothell; Megan Bang,
Northwestern University; Anna Lees, University of
Washington; Carrie T. Tzou, University of Washington -
Bothell; Shirin Vossoughi, Northwestern University;
Charlene Montano Nolan, Western Washington University
4. Fostering Elementary Students' Perspectives of the Natural
World Through Playful Co-design (Poster 4). *Zachary D.*
Ryan, Indiana University
5. Exploring Human and More-Than-Human
Interconnectedness in Higher Education through the Arts
(Poster 5). *Yisha Zhao, University of Washington*
6. Disability Representation in Nature-Themed Board Books
(Poster 6). *Caitlin Tobin, University of Wisconsin - Madison*
7. Listening Like Moss: A Live Mosscast Recording as
Multispecies Pedagogy in Performance (Poster 7). *Brandon*
Edwards-Schuth, Augusta University; Anna Vladimirova,
University of Oulu; Marina Pliushchik, University of Oulu;
Maria Helena Saari, University of Oulu
8. Re-imagining Multispecies Futures in Environmental
Education: Children's Lived Experiences of Intuitive
Interspecies Communication with Animals (Poster 8).
Megan Tucker, Simon Fraser University
9. Locust History for Future Teachers: A Relational
Approach to California's Environmental Principles and
Concepts (Poster 9). *Jeannette Vaught, California State*

University - Los Angeles

10. 10. Living, Learning, and Teaching with Chickens: Unforgetting Southern California's Agrohistories to Enact Transformative Futures (Poster 10). *Teresa Lloro, California State Polytechnic University - Pomona; Jillian Muñoz, California State Polytechnic University - Pomona*
11. 11 "He's Coming to Say Hello to You!" The Impact of Teacher Discourse on Children's Understanding of Animals (Poster 11). *Patty Born, Hamline University*
12. 12. What's in a Name? Deconstructing "Nonhuman" through Multiple Lenses and Implications for Futuring Environmental Education (Poster 12). *Sean Blenkinsop, Simon Fraser University; Megan Tucker, Simon Fraser University*

Chair: *Emily Holm Tobin, University of Washington*

Discussant: *Anne Katherine Armstrong, Worcester State University*

22.044. Families and postsecondary students: Relationships and engagement. SIG-Family, School, Community Partnerships; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum B; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

- How Digital Literacy and Family Communication Shape Adult Coping with Cyberbullying: A Network Analysis. *Qiqi Chen, Hong Kong Polytechnic University*
- Letters of Aspiration: Family Narratives and the Cultural Wealth of First-Generation College Students. *Stephany Cuevas, Chapman University; Athina Cuevas, Chapman University*
- A Qualitative Study of GEAR UP's Role in School-Community Partnerships. *Meghan Ecker-Lyster, University of Kansas; Amelia Murray, University of Kansas; Sabrina C. Gregersen, PYMNTS*

Centering Family Voices in School Psychology Training: Examining the Impact on Students' Learning. *Terese Aceves, Loyola Marymount University*

Valuing Family, Mentorship, and Joy: Career Learning Experiences of Middle School Prospective First-Generation College Students. *Nina R. Schoonover, University of Virginia; Russell Carlock, Albemarle County Public Schools; Joseph M. Williams, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Ben Allen, University of Virginia*

Chair: *Diana Marcela Galvez Bohorquez, San Francisco Unified School District*

Discussant: *Theresa A. Meyerott, California State University - Los Angeles*

22.045. Imagining Futures: Themes of Decolonization, Empowerment, and Mentorship within Indigenous Contexts in Education. SIG-Indigenous Peoples of the Pacific and Beyond; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 3;

11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

- Stories of Multigenerational Resistance to Internalized Oppression within a Majority-Hawaiian Community. *Kourtney Kawano, University of California - Berkeley*
- The Academy as a Settler Nexus: A Global Analysis of Indigenous Experiences in Higher Education. *Levon Ghanimian, Claremont Graduate University*
- Mentorship as Resistance: Cultivating Indigenous Leadership in the Face of Historical Injustice. *Margaret J. Maaka, University of Hawai'i at Manoa; Huia Tomlins Jahnke, Massey University; Kekailoa Perry, University of Hawai'i at Mānoa; Kerry Laiana Wong, University of Hawai'i at Manoa; Patricia Maringi Gina Johnston-Ak, Te Whare Wananga o Awanuiarangi*
- Filipinos in Hawai'i: Pathways to Decolonization and Empowerment. *Phillippe Rivera Fernandez-Brennan, Halau Ku Mana*

Chair: *Ivy Kahukiwa Smith, Te Kōpere o te Iwi o Hineuru*

Discussants: *Sharon Nelson-Barber, WestEd; Kamuela M. Kimoeko, Windward Community College*

22.046. Power and Learning in Museums: Reimagining Museums as Sites of Untold Histories. SIG-Informal Learning Environment Research; Paper Session

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, La Cienega; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

- Applying Universal Design for Learning to Create Inclusive Museum Activities for Neurodiverse Audiences. *Susan M. Letourneau, New York Hall of Science; Wendy B. Martin, Education Development Center, Inc.; Samantha Tumolo, Education Development Center, Inc.; Dana Schloss, New York Hall of Science; Amelia Merker, New York Hall of Science; Tara Henderson, Explora; Danielle Linzer, Children's Museum of Pittsburgh*
- Food as a Catalyst for Positional Fluidity among Youth and Caregivers in the Participatory Design of a Food-Culture STEM Demonstration in a Science Center. *Phebe Chew, New York Hall of Science*
- Meaningful Learning with Zines at the Punk Rock Museum: A Mixed-Methods Study. *April Ursula Fox, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*
- Migration Museums as Sites of Civic Learning: Exploring Global Citizenship Education in Three Countries. *Daria Smirnova, University of South Florida*
- The Co-construction of Power and Learning in a Museum Exhibit about Climate Change. *Kaitlyn Kinshella, University of Utah; Lynne Zummo, University of Utah*

Chair: *Lynne Zummo, University of Utah*

22.047. Linguistic M(other)work as Pedagogy, Resistance, and Disruption: Language and Immigrant Futurity in Education Research. SIG-Language and Social Processes;

Symposium

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 506;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Liderazgo & Linguaging: Maya Mam Women's Practices of
Survivance in Diaspora. *Cristina Selena Mendez, University
of California - Berkeley*

Recuerdos Caminantes: Mother-Daughter Mappings of Pasts
and Futures Through Language. *Sarah Perez, University of
California - Los Angeles*

In Search of Standard English: Accent and Prescriptivism as
Linguistic Tools for Immigrant Mothers and Family
Futurity. *Jackson Gzehoviak, University of California - Los
Angeles; Flora Zempleni, University of California - Los
Angeles*

Rooted in Amistades! M(other)work for Language, Learning,
and Thriving in the U.S. *Sophia Piral Lee, University of
Missouri*

Chairs: *Flora Zempleni, University of California - Los Angeles;
Jackson Gzehoviak, University of California - Los Angeles*

Discussant: *Cati V. de los Rios, University of California - Berkeley*

22.048. Equity Work in the Current Moment. SIG-Leadership
for Social Justice; Symposium

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Los Cerritos; 11:45am to
1:15pm

Participants:

Sustaining Equity Work in an Anti-Equity Context. *John B.
Diamond, Brown University; Emily Handsman, Rutgers
University; Jordan Mosby; Emily Nott, University of
Wisconsin - Madison*

District Leaders' Strategies for Sustaining Equity Work in the
Face of Obstacles. *Caleb Probst, University of Wisconsin -
Madison*

What They Talked About When Talking About Equity:
Discourse in Principal Pipeline Work. *Aziz Awaludin,
University of Wisconsin - Madison; Daniella Molle,
University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Chair: *Daniella Molle, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Discussant: *Francesca López, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

**22.049. Unforgetting Legal Precedent: Illuminating the Roots
of Discrimination and Forging Equitable Futures in
Education.** SIG-Multicultural/Multiethnic Education:
Theory, Research and Practice; Symposium

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Georgia II;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Blueprints for Belonging: Black Students' Aspirations and the
Architecture of College Futures. *Tr'Vel Lyons, University of
Southern California*

Race, Gender, and Faith: Addressing Gendered Islamophobia in
Higher Education. *Milie Majumder, University of Southern
California*

Asian American and Latinx College Experiences and DEL.

Mabel Eunice Hernandez, University of Southern California;

Alana Aiko Uilani Kennedy, Northern Arizona University

An Intergenerational STEM Mentorship Program's Impacts on
Advancing Equity and Title IX for Female Students. *Ting-
Han Chang, William Paterson University*

Chair: *Darnell G. Cole, University of Southern California*

Discussant: *Shafiqah Ahmadi, University of Southern California*

22.050. Democracy and Ethics. SIG-Philosophical Studies in
Education; Paper Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304B;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

"Covert No-Saying": A Framework of Democratic Education in
Illiberal Democracies. *Jason Cong Lin, The Education
University of Hong Kong*

Identifying Democratic Distance in School Authority. *Thomas J
Capretta, The Ohio State University*

Listening to Prevent Educational Displacement: A Case Study.
*Vikramaditya Joshi, Columbia University; Amra Sabic-El-
Rayess, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Markets, Education, and Community. *David O'Brien,
University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Reconstructing Educational Democracy: From Rousseau's
General Will to Agonistic General Will. *Yawen Xie, East
China Normal University*

Chair: *Jawanza Kalonji Rand, Teachers College, Columbia
University*

**22.051. Bridging the Gap: An Afrofuturist Vision for STEM
Education.** SIG-Research Focus on Black Education; Paper
Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 411
(Theatre); 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Afrofuturism and STEM: An Intersectional Framework for
Equity and Innovation. *Zariah Nicole, Johns Hopkins
University; Devin T. White, Johns Hopkins University;*

*Ebony O. McGee, Johns Hopkins University; Thema
Monroe-White, George Mason University*

All my people spiritual: Maintaining communalistic values to
support the STEM matriculation of black men. *Takeshia
Pierre, Tufts University; Neisha Terry Young, Stony Brook
University - SUNY*

Bridging The Gap: A Comparative Case Study of STEM
Education At An HBCU And A PWI. *Ebony Terrell
Shockley, University of Maryland; Jeffery S. Fleming,
University of the District of Columbia; Fredric Ratliff,
University of the District of Columbia*

When We Build Together: Supporting Black STEM Majors'
Transformation Into STEM Educators. *Tabora Johnson,
Medger Evers College - CUNY; Salika A. Lawrence, SAL
Consulting, LLC; Chiyedza Small, Medgar Evers College,*

City University of New York

Chair: *Franklin A. Soares, United Negro College Fund*

22.052. Dreaming Beyond Numbers: Storytelling as a Methodology and Praxis in Mathematics Education. SIG-Research in Mathematics Education; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum A; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Sifting Meaning from Data: Integrating Computational Text Analysis into Qualitative Inquiry. *Nathan Alexander, Howard University; Darnell Leatherwood, University of Michigan*

Collective Dreaming as Methodology: How Storytelling Workshops Transform Mathematics Education Through Shared Imagination. *Blake O'Neal Turner, Marquette University; Rolonda L. Payne, University of Maryland*

Dreaming in Tandem: A Duoethnographic Inquiry into Spiritual Praxis and Justice-Centered Mathematics Futures. *David J. Wallace, Awakening Minds LLC; Candace Kyles, Loyola University Chicago*

Chair: *Nathan Alexander, Howard University*

Discussant: *Blake O'Neal Turner, Marquette University*

22.053. Academic Mothers. SIG-Research on Women and Education; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 504; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

"Nobody Was Advocating for Me": Academic Mothers' Experiences Navigating Institutional Leave Policies. *Kelly W. Guyotte, University of Alabama; Diana Quito, Rollins College; Venus Trevaue Watson, University of Alabama*

Academic Mothers: A Study of Work-life Challenges. *Lu Liang, Pepperdine University*

Empowerment and Healing: A Duoethnographic Study on Two International Doctoral Student-Mothers in the U.S. *Xiaoyi Wei, SUNY Brockport; Qinghua Liu, Boston College*

Motherhood as Pedagogical Praxis in Teacher Education: Teacher Educator Mothers Leveraging Motherhood in Their Teaching. *Eugenia Vomvoridi-Ivanovic, University of South Florida; Sarah A. van Ingen Lauer, University of South Florida; Jennifer Ward, Kennesaw State University; Cheryl R. Ellerbrock, University of South Florida; Sophia Han, University of South Florida; Karina K. R. Hensberry, University of South Florida; Jennifer Jacobs, University of South Florida; Patriann Smith, University of South Florida*

Navigating motherhood and academia as an international doctoral student. *Ainur Jumagaliyeva, University of Minnesota*

22.054. Building Inclusive Futures: Teachers Advancing Equity through Social and Emotional Learning in Diverse Learning Contexts. SIG-Social and Emotional

Learning; Symposium

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, San Bernardino; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Nurturing Little Hearts and Minds: Rural Teachers' Approaches to Culturally Responsive Social and Emotional Learning.

Xueqin Lin, University of California - Berkeley; Josephine Ingram, University of California - Berkeley

Early Learning of Lego Robotics and STEM through Culturally Responsive Social and Emotional Learning. *Jabari Mahiri, University of California - Berkeley*

Teachers' Perspectives of Developmentally Appropriate Transformative Social and Emotional Learning in Elementary and Secondary Schools. *Jin Hyung Lim, University of California - Berkeley*

Leaves on the Jocko River: Engaging Teacher Social and Emotional Learning in Indigenous Communities. *Jingjing Sun, University of Montana; Anisa Goforth, University of Montana; Deborah Ith, University of Montana - Missoula*

Chair: *Xueqin Lin, University of California - Berkeley*

Discussant: *Chunyan Yang, University of Maryland*

22.055. Connections, Expectations and Fit: Institutional Agents and Student Success. SIG-Sociology of Education; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 501C; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

"I Want Y'all to Succeed": Cultural Logics and the Complex Nature of Teacher Expectations. *Maia B. Cucchiara, Temple University; Sherelle Ferguson, University of California - Irvine; Sidra Sheikh, The Center for Program Design and Evaluation*

Mediating "Fit" in International College Admissions Consulting. *Swati Puri, Harvard University*

Qualitative Study of Counselors as Social Capital Agents for Undocumented/Citizen Students from Mixed-Status Families. *Jenifer L. Kelson, Claremont Graduate University*

Chair: *Stuart Rhoden, Arizona State University*

22.056. Spiritual explorations in the 21st century. SIG-Spirituality & Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum I; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

A duoethnography on teaching the complexities of spirituality: "Not the shark, but in the water". *Ricardo Montelongo, Sam Houston State University; J. Cody Nielsen, Western Michigan University*

The Power of Spiritual Engagement: Enhancing Emotional Health in STEM College Students. *Young K. Kim, Azusa Pacific University; Jeff Clawson, Council for Christian Colleges and Universities*

Religious Teachers' Perspectives on Resilience, Student Well-

being, and Learning Five Years After the Pandemic. *Lorelei R. Coddington, Biola University; Candace Jewell, Biola University*

Theorizing Spiritual Capital Through the Lived Experiences of Black Women Doctoral Students. *Jodi Lynne Patton-Jordan, Southern Illinois University - Edwardsville; Lori Patton Davis, University of California, Los Angeles*

Discussant: *Judy A. Alston, Miami University (OH)*

22.057. Instructional Leadership and Mentorship:

Frameworks, Challenges, and Impacts. SIG-Supervision and Instructional Leadership; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Level 2, Echo Park; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

A Conceptual Framework for Virtual Mentoring and Coaching of School Leaders. *Roya Pashmforoosh, Texas A&M University; Beverly J. Irby, Texas A&M University; Rafael Lara-Alecio, Texas A&M University*

Instructional Supervision as Liberation: Culturally Responsive Mentorship Through National Board Facilitation. *Honey Walrond, University of California - Berkeley; Travis J. Bristol, University of California - Berkeley*

The Challenges of Instructional Leadership in Remote Contexts: A Case Study. *Maria A. Flores, University of Minho*

The Influence of Instructional Leadership on Instructional Practice: A Mediation Analysis of Teacher Self-Efficacy. *Arinze Anselm Ezirim, University of Utah; Yongmei Ni, University of Utah*

22.058. Cognition, Emotion, Motivation, and Creativity:

Evidence for Holistic Learning Design. SIG-Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis; Paper Session
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Echo Park; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Effects of Positive Psychology Interventions in Second Language Learning and Well-being A Systematic Meta-Analytic Review. *Xinjie Chen, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Maisie GLOFCHESKI, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Zhenyi ZHOU, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Jean Marc Dewaele, University of London*

Fostering Creative Thinking through Interdisciplinary Teaching: A Meta-Analysis of Effectiveness. *Xingpeng Zhang, East China Normal University; Shaohui Chi, East China Normal University; Zuhao Wang, East China Normal University*

Heterogeneity in the Effects of Formative Assessment on Self-Regulated Learning: A Meta-Analysis. *Elie Chingyen Yu, University at Albany - SUNY; Heidi L. Andrade, University at Albany - SUNY; YangHyun Kim, City University of New York; Wim Van den Noortgate, KU Leuven; Mariola Moeyaert, University at Albany - SUNY; Angela M. Lui,*

CUNY - School of Professional Studies; Diana Akhmedjanova, National Research University "Higher School of Economics"; Dylan R. Wiliam, UCL Institute of Education

Self-Directed Learning with Mobile-Assisted Language Learning: A Meta-Analysis of Its Effectiveness and Key Moderators to Inform Decision-Making. *Adnan Mayof, Washington State University*

Psychosocial Interventions to Improve Postsecondary Student Mathematics Attainment: A Scoping Review. *Carlton J. Fong, Texas State University; Taylor W. Acee, Texas State University; Semilore F. Adelugba, Texas State University; Sanzida Sharmeen, Texas State University; Pedram Zarei, Texas State University; Zohreh Fathi, Texas State University; Pegah Peimani, Texas State University; IMANEH SOLEIMANI, Texas State University*

Chair: *Xue Wang, Johns Hopkins University*

Division and SIG Roundtables

22.059. AERA Roundtable Session Wednesday 11:45 am;
Roundtable Session

22.059-1. Agency as decolonial praxis in curriculum (Table 1).

Division B - Curriculum Studies; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

From Critical Reading to Critical Consciousness: Toward a Decolonizing Curriculum. *Elizabeth Isidro, Western Michigan University; Eric Claravall, California State University - Sacramento*

About Us, By Us: Collaborative Curriculum Development for Reparative Action. *Tiferet Ani, University of Pennsylvania; Krystal Strong, Rutgers University*

Co-Curricular-Making: "Rallying the World Around the Future of Education". *Margaret A. Macintyre Latta, University of British Columbia - Okanagan; William A. Cohen, University of British Columbia - Okanagan; Danielle Lamb, University of British Columbia - Okanagan*

Silences in Climate Education: Epistemic Injustice and De/Colonial Curriculum in British Columbia. *Tamanna Maqsood, University of British Columbia*

Chair: *Elizabeth Isidro, Western Michigan University*

22.059-2. Black Educational Strivings: Boyhood, Resistance, and Living History (Table 2).

Division F - Historical Inquiry in Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Black Boy Innocence: A Portraiture of Urban Waldorf School. *Andre Spencer Anderson-Thompson, University of*

California - Davis

“Blessed are the Peacemakers” Brown and the Catholic School.
Katrina M. Sanders, University of Iowa

Booker T. Washington High School: A Living History (1950 - Present). *Tracy D. Freeman, University of Virginia*
Remembering the Freedom Summer of 1964 to Avoid Making the Same Mistakes Again. *Hani Morgan, University of Southern Mississippi*

Chair: *Charles T. Young, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

22.059-3. Critical Education in an International Context (Table 3). Division F - Historical Inquiry in Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Assimilation as Expansion: U.S. Schooling of American Indians, Filipinos, and Chinese around the Century’s Turn.

Yu Wang, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign

Hidden Reefs Beneath the Rising Island: An Analysis of Higher Education Expansion in India. *Mingyang Guo, Xiamen University*

Scientific Diaspora as Reformers: German-Jewish Scholars and Institutional Change in 1930s Türkiye. *Seyma Aksoy, Yildiz Technical University Türkiye*

"Unforgetting Resistance: Algeria as a Case Study." *Somia Somia Hammadi, Hassiba Benbouali University*

Unforgetting the Literary Histories of Azerbaijan: Identity, Power, and Imagination from Empire to Independence. *Shafiq Dadashova, ADA University*

Chair: *Sabahet S. Bruncaj, United Arab Emirates University*

22.059-4. Critical Theories of Educational Histories (Table 4). Division F - Historical Inquiry in Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

A Critical Historical Analysis of Latina/o/x Activism and Response by the Campus Community. *Ebelia Hernandez, Rutgers University*

Cultural Material and Mass Media Dissemination as the Foundations of White Supremacy Among Changing Populations. *Robert Kenlaw, Notre Dame of Maryland University*

New Ways of Seeing: A Response to Tyack. *Max Jacobs, Rutgers University*

The Enduring and Taken-for-Granted Impact of the Grade-Level Structure of American Education. *Deborah Loewenberg Ball, University of Michigan; Mike Henderson, University of Michigan*

What Would Adorno Say?: Seeing the Current Right Wing Attack on Education through Theodor Adorno's Eyes. *Eric J.*

Weiner, Montclair State University

Chair: *Brandon J. Beck, University of Maryland Baltimore County*

22.059-5. Teacher Efficacy, Mentorship and Cultural Responsiveness (Table 5). Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Bilingual Culturally Responsive Teacher Efficacy through a Collective Framework. *Ana M. Hernandez, California State University - San Marcos; Annette M. Daoud, California State University - San Marcos; Xochitl Archey, California State University - San Marcos*

Latinx Undergraduate Mentors’ Experiences in an Asset-based After-School Program. *Carla Suarez Soto, University of California - Santa Cruz*

Testimonios of Latinx Mentors: Challenging Deficit Views Through Culturally Responsive Mentorship. *Carla Suarez Soto, University of California - Santa Cruz; Isabella Hernandez, University of California - Santa Cruz; Karina Sarahy Hernandez, University of California - Santa Cruz; Mayte Flores Ortega, University of California - Santa Cruz*

Chair: *Jubara AbuSin, Pennsylvania State University*

22.059-6. “Seeing” Social Contexts through Innovative Methodologies (Table 6). Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Boundless fields of relation: Reconceptualizing pláticas beyond methods and methodology. *Eric Alvarez, Arizona State University; Reyna Paulina Cruz Valenzuela, Pomona College*

“Everywhere You Ain’t:” Visual Ethnographic Approaches to Place-based Cultural Practice in Los Angeles. *Brian Zamora, University of California - Los Angeles*

Images that Dehumanize: Deconstructing and deposing ableism in Special Education curriculum. *Michael Edmond Skyer, University of Tennessee; David M Bowers, University of Tennessee; Leah Oakes, University of Tennessee*

Reading Against The Grain; Examining Student Journalism for Glimpses of Black Life. *Bethany Bass, Stanford University*

Chair: *Laura Fittz Parks, Fort Lewis College*

22.059-7. Mentoring, Training, Measurement & Technology (Table 7). SIG-Mentorship and Mentoring Practices; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

From Busy Work to Purposeful Research: How Mentor Training Influences Undergraduate Experiences and Career

Aspirations. Heather McCall, University of Kentucky; Cameron Richards, University of Kentucky; Jennifer A. Wilhelm, University of Kentucky; Christopher Crawford, University of Kentucky; Max Brown, University of Kentucky

Mentoring as a Two-Way Street: Scale Validation Assessing Performance Among Undergraduate Mentees and Faculty Mentors. *Constanza Miranda, Johns Hopkins University; Rachel Saperstein McClam, Johns Hopkins University; Paulina Perez Mejias, Johns Hopkins University*

Affective Language Patterns in Text-Based Communication Predict Relational Outcomes in Online-Mentoring for Girls in STEM. *Claudia Uebler, University of Regensburg; Albert Ziegler, Friedrich-Alexander-University of Erlangen-Nürnberg; Heidrun Stoeger, University of Regensburg*

Reviewing the Literature on Mentoring Underrepresented Minority Students in STEM. *Lehong Shi, University of Georgia; Ikseon Choi, Emory University; Janette R. Hill, University of Georgia; James Lauderdale, University of Georgia*

Chair: *Michael A. Hunt, University of Maryland - Baltimore County*

22.060. AERA Roundtable Session Wednesday 11:45 am - Gold 1; Roundtable Session

22.060-1. Roundtable Session 2: Student Learning and Development in College and Beyond (Table 1). Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

AI Literacy and LLM Engagement in Higher Education: A Cross-National Quantitative Study. *Shahin Hossain, University of Maryland - Baltimore County; Samaa Haniya, Pepperdine University; Nesma Ragab Nasr, Northern Arizona University; Shapla Khanam, HELP University*

Constructing New Possibilities for Literature Reviews: Assessing the Binning Method in Scholarly Inquiry. *Audrey Amrein-Beardsley, Arizona State University; Norman P. Gibbs, Mesa Unified School District*

How Does Online Learning Affect College Students' Deep Learning: A Study Using Data from China. *Liu Jingjing, Xiamen University; Shutao Wang, Xiamen University*

More Than Pedagogy: Centering Student Experiences in Culturally Responsive STEM Gateway Courses. *Alice Eunjung Lee, University of Texas - El Paso*

22.060-2. Who is Shaping Institutions: The Role of External Organizations and Philanthropy (Table 2). Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

How Can We Help? – Philanthropic Problem Brokers

Advancing Equity in the Aftermath of a Blackface Scandal. *Pooja R. Patel, University of Pennsylvania*

Into the Rabbit Hole: Understanding the Enigmatic Flow of Foreign Funds into U.S. Universities. *Jacob Goldstein, Baruch College; Ryan Coughlan, Baruch College - CUNY*

Meaning Making of Grant-Funded Spaces at an Asian American and Pacific Islander (AAPI)-Serving Community College. *Victoria Kim, University of Texas - San Antonio*

22.060-3. Division J Section 6: Roundtable 1 (Table 3). Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Erasing gender and race demographics: A critical discourse analysis of law school class profiles. *Khadejah Ray, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Megan Holland Iantosca, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Karly Ford, Pennsylvania State University*

Implicit Racial Bias and Campus Culture at Predominantly White Institutions. *Edwin Mathieu, New York University*

Inclusive Excellence or Everyday Exclusion? Experiences of Faculty, Staff and Students of Color with Racial Microaggressions on a Campus Committed to Inclusive Excellence. *Lindsay Pérez Huber, California State University - Long Beach; Carlos Fitch, University of California - Santa Barbara; Oscar Navarro, California State University - Long Beach*

New Title: Oral History as Power, Method, and Archive: Centering Black Leadership in Community. *Dre'Sha T. Singleton, North Carolina State University; Devon Lomes Graves, North Carolina State University*

22.060-4. The Work of Becoming: Growth, Identity, and Professional Fulfillment in Education (Table 4). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Identity and Practice: A Collaborative Autoethnography of Two Transnational Teacher Educators of Color. *David D. Yang, Western Washington University; Meilan Jin, Western Washington University*

Imagining the Academic Self: Identity, Intersectionality, and Aspiration in Doctoral Student Development. *Arpana Manjunath, University of Houston; Lebon D. James, Sam Houston State University; Mandana Delavari, University of Houston; Patrick Obot, University of Houston*

Unforgetting the Labor of Becoming: Reclaiming Histories and Futures of Adult Learners in Teacher Education. *Laura A. Roy, La Salle University*

Unlocking Teaching Satisfaction: The Role of Faculty Growth Mindset, Person-Organization Fit, and Demographic Nuances. *Ning Ning, Shanghai Jiao Tong University; Xin*

Gao, Shanghai Jiao Tong University; Zhu Yanmin, Shanghai Jiao Tong University; Tingting Zhang, Shanghai Jiao Tong University; Shuai Wang, Shanghai Jiao Tong University

Chair: David D. Yang, Western Washington University

22.060-5. School Boards as Sites of Discourse, Legitimation, and Racialized Institutional Logics Amid Democratic Unrest (Table 5). Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

California School Boards and Their Members' Experiences in Dynamic Times. *Beth Schueler, University of Virginia; Julie A. Marsh, University of Southern California; James C. Bridgeforth, University of Delaware; Jeimee Estrada-Miller, University of Southern California*

The Tensions of Technological Shifts on School Board Governance and Practice. *James C. Bridgeforth, University of Delaware; Akunna Faith Uka, University of Southern California; Amanda Lauren Pickett, University of Delaware; Julie A. Marsh, University of Southern California; Miguel Casar, University of Alabama; Laura Steen Mulfinger, University of Southern California; Jacob Alonso, University of Southern California*

"It's Like Cutting Down a Beautiful Tree and Putting it in Concrete": Examining the Logics Shaping a School Merger Debate. *Esi Bissah, University of California - Irvine; Jomar M. Lopes, University of California - Irvine; Eupha Jeanne Daramola, University of California - Irvine*

(De-)Legitimizing Ethnic Studies: A Discourse Analysis of Board-Community Member Interactions. *Jomar M. Lopes, University of California - Irvine*

How School Boards Utilize Organizational Routines During Moments of Tension. *Eupha Jeanne Daramola, University of California - Irvine; James C. Bridgeforth, University of Delaware*

Chair: *Eupha Jeanne Daramola, University of California - Irvine*

Discussant: *Sarah L. Woulfin, University of Texas at Austin*

22.060-6. Segregation and Peer Diversity: New Evidence on their Sources and Impacts (Table 6). Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Does Same-Race Representation or Racial Diversity Matter More? Evidence from Peer Composition and Reading Outcomes in U.S. Elementary Schools. *Daman Chhikara, University of California - Irvine*

The Impact of Centralized Admission School Lotteries on School Segregation. *Jason Saltmarsh, Old Dominion University; Francisco Lagos, Inter-American Development Bank; Jing Liu, University of Maryland*

The Segregation of Multilingual Learners in North Carolina. *Cassandra Rubinstein, North Carolina State University; Victor Cadilla, North Carolina State University; Mary Kathryn Oyaga, North Carolina State University*

Gentrification Moves Outward: The Changing Terrain of School Poverty and Suburban Segregation. *Hyojung Lee, Seoul National University; Kfir Mordechay, Pepperdine University*

Chair: *Jin Lee, University of Louisiana at Lafayette*

22.060-7. Unforgetting Childhood: Policy, Practice, and the Futures of Early Learning (Table 7). Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Children's Right to Play: Lessons from the United Kingdom, Ireland, and Finland for Taiwan. *Yulun Hsieh, National Sun Yat-sen University; Chih-Ching Chang, National Sun Yat-sen University*

Examining Preschool Expansion's Impact on Child Care Closures: A Difference-in-Difference Approach in Multiple State Contexts. *Jennifer K. Duer, National Institute for Early Education Research; Allison Friedman-Krauss, National Institute for Early Education Research; Milagros Nores, Rutgers University*

Family Perspectives of the Initial Implementation of an Equity-Focused Universal Preschool Program. *Dede Addy, Boston University; Desiree' DuBoise, Portland State University; Melissa Lucas, Yale University; Kyle DeMeo Cook, Boston University; Stephanie M. Curenton, Boston University; Xia Zhang, Multnomah County; Janice Cole, Multnomah County*

Long-term Substitute Teachers in NC Pre-K Classrooms. *Qiao Liu, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Kristen E. Wright, University of North Carolina at Charlotte; Richard G. Lambert, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Onima Vadakke Thodiyil, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Katherine Jiawen Ren, University of North Carolina - Charlotte*

Chair: *Maria Mavrides Calderon, Hunter College - CUNY*

22.060-8. Labor of Love, Weight of Care: Emotional Realities in Early Childhood Classrooms (Table 8). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Daily Dynamics of Job Stressors, Emotion Regulation, and Well-Being Among Kindergarten Teachers. *Yi Sun, National Institute of Education, Nanyang Technological University; Hongbiao Yin, The Chinese University of Hong Kong*

Depression and Stress among Early Child Care and Education Professionals: Results from Three Nationwide Surveys. *Ayşe Cobanoglu, Bogazici University; Walter Gilliam, Yale*

University

Early Elementary Educators Tending to Nostalgia: A Discourse Analysis of Educators' Perspectives. *Katherine Davenport, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Understanding Emotion Beliefs in Early Childhood Educators: The Role of Equity Mindsets and Psychosocial Strain. *Javier Omar, Stanford University; Kavindya Thennakoon, Stanford University; Catie Connolly, Stanford University; Jelena Obradovic, Stanford University*

Chair: *Ayse Cobanoglu, Bogazici University*

22.060-9. The Politics of Becoming: Subjectivity, Power, and Teacher Formation (Table 9). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Decolonizing Practices and Teacher Sense of Place in an Indigenous space. *Josef Donnelly, University of Hawai'i at Hilo*

Future Teachers of Color at Critical Junctures: Centering Equity in Teacher Preparation in Community College. *Leticia Rojas, Pasadena City College*

In-Between and Becoming: Positionality, Power, and Justice in Teacher Education. *Ayesha Rabadi-Raol, Sonoma State University*

Origin Story of a Teacher: A Decolonial Feminist Critical Whiteness Autoethnography. *Carol Ann Opie, Michigan State University*

Teacher Subjectivity Through Difficult Knowledge: A Lacanian Analysis. *Monika Mehta, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Chair: *Josef Donnelly, University of Hawai'i at Hilo*

22.061. AERA Roundtable Session Wednesday 11:45 am - Gold 2; Roundtable Session

22.061-1. Middle School Students' Engagement in Civic Education (Table 1). SIG-Democratic Citizenship in Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

8th-graders' Expressions of Civic Efficacy Upon Completion of a Yearlong Student-led Civics Curriculum. *Natalie Sew, Harvard University; Ariana Zetlin, University of Pennsylvania*

"I Don't Love This, But ...": How Middle Schoolers Practice Democratic Citizenship During Action Civics. *Michelle Bauml, Texas Christian University; Victoria Smith, University of North Texas; Jerrett Lyday, Texas Christian University*

Chair: *Elisabeth Graf, TU Dortmund University*

22.061-2. Experiential Education and Community Engagement: Scholarship and Practice SIG Roundtable 1 (Table 2). SIG-Experiential Education and Community Engagement: Scholarship and Practice; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Collective Witnessing and Committing to Action: Enhancing Student Reflection in Short-Term Study Abroad. *William Pryor, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*

Engaging Teenagers in Community-Centered Edge AI Projects. *Andrea Ramirez-Salgado, University of Florida; Lauren Eutsler, University of North Texas; Anany Sharma, University of Florida; Woorin Hwang, University of Florida; Yessy Eka Ambarwati, University of Florida; Talar Terzian, University of Florida; Megan Barnes, University of North Texas; Nicole Dominguez, University of Florida; Dillon Donihue, University of Florida; Swarup Bhunia, University of Florida; Tamzidul Hoque, University of Kansas; Pasha Antonenko, University of Florida*

Exploring Experiential Learning: A Duoethnographic Study on US Preservice Teachers in Costa Rica. *Katya Koubek, James Madison University*

Implementing Community-engaged Learning as a Campus-wide Initiative at an R-1 Institution. *Mellinee K. Lesley, Texas Tech University*

Chair: *Vanessa Hammler Kenon, University of Texas - San Antonio*

22.061-3. Troubling Histories and Complicating Identities (Table 3). SIG-Music Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Activism Through Queer Joy: A Collaborative Autoethnography of Queer & Nonbinary Music Teacher Educators. *Justin M. Caithaml, University of Bridgeport; Austin Norrid, Ohio University*

Beyond Binaries: Agency and Musical Identity in Chinese American Immigrant Children's Ecological Systems. *Xin Xie, Macau University of Science and Technology*

Considering The New Trail: Survivance, Music Education, and the Phoenix Indian School. *Shawn T. Kimbrel, Arizona State University*

The Lived Experiences of Chinese Older Adults in an Invented String Instrumental Classroom. *Cancan Cui, Guangzhou University*

Troubling Binaries, Imagining Futurities: Toward Non-Binary Thinking in Music Education in Polarized Times. *Saleel Menon, Michigan State University; Lorenzo Sánchez-Gatt, Boston University; Juliet Hess, Michigan State University*

Chair: *Darrin Thornton, Pennsylvania State University*

22.061-4. Strengthening Teacher Growth and Student Learning through School–University Partnerships: Perceptions, Professional Learning, and Mentorship (Table 4). SIG-School-University Partnership Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Mentoring High School Researchers: An Examination of the Experiences of University Faculty as Mentors. *Jilliane McCardle, Eastern Kentucky University; Christopher Budano, Eastern Kentucky University; Peter Edwards, Eastern Kentucky University*

Transforming Students' School Experiences through Teachers' Sustained Professional Learning. *Yun-chen Yen, Pennsylvania State University; Danielle Butville, Pennsylvania State University*

Developing Teachers' Perceptions, Practices, and Self-efficacy of Culture-Teaching through School-University Partnership. *Wai Ming Cheung, University of Hong Kong; Serene Chan, University of Hong Kong; Lanfang Sun, University of Hong Kong; Hector W. H. Tsang, Hong Kong Polytechnic University*

22.061-5. Critical Multilingual Education Around the Globe: Identity, Self-Efficacy, and Raciolinguistics in International Contexts (Table 5). SIG-Second Language Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Bicultural Identity Integration and Ideal L2 Self: Influencing Chinese L2 Learning in Multilingual Hong Kong. *Wanru Pang, The Hong Kong Polytechnic University; Siyu Zhu, The Hong Kong Polytechnic University; Xinhua Zhu, Hong Kong Polytechnic University; Ziqi Zhang, Hong Kong Polytechnic University*

International College Students' Perceived English Language Competence and Academic Self-Efficacy in the U.S. Midwest. *Maria Zaman, University of North Dakota*

Pseudo-Translanguaging: Raciolinguistic Perspectives on White Supremacy in English Language Teaching in Asia. *Yin Lam Lee-Johnson, Webster University; Yi-Ju Lai, University of Minnesota*

Reframing Assessments for Emergent Bilinguals: A Holistic Bilingual and Translanguaging Pedagogy Approach. *Angeles Munoz, University of North Texas / Texas Woman's University*

Chair: *Matt DeRoo, Florida International University*

Discussant: *Matt DeRoo, Florida International University*

22.061-6. Discourse Analysis Across Language Education Contexts: Examining Textbooks, Policy, and Colonial Narratives (Table 6). SIG-Second Language Research;

Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Access to linguistic inclusion? A critical discourse analysis of Oregon's HB 2056. *Jaelyn B. Bovee, Oregon State University*

Stories of Displacement: Analyzing War, Refugees, and Immigrants in Children's Picture Books with English as a Global Language. *Robby Anggriawan, Illinois State University*

Enhancing Cultural Awareness in Teaching Effectiveness of Situation-bound Utterances: A CSL Textbook Analysis. *Ying Kong, University at Albany - SUNY*

Multimodal Discourse as Colonial Control: An Analysis of Japanese Language Textbooks for Chinese Students in 1935-1936. *Yuqing Sun, New York University*

22.061-7. Bilingualism desde el corazón to the enactment of languaging (Table 7). SIG-Bilingual Education Research; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Una Paraeducadora Bilingüe en ELA: A Bilingual Paraeducator Mediates a Library-based Reading Group. *Elizabeth Castro, Central Washington University*

When Hearts Beat in Two Languages: Elementary Bilingual Pathways Recognitions for Latine Linguistically Expanding Learners. *Mayra C Orozco, Claremont Graduate University*

Translanguaging Pedagogies in Linguistically Diverse, Newcomer-serving Secondary Classrooms: Implications of Educators' Conceptions of Equity. *Kelley Riffenburgh, University of California - Irvine*

"El Lenguaje Se Queda En La Casa": Family Literacy and HL Preservation in a Spanish and Kaqchikel Immigrant Household. *Esmeralda Cartagena Collazo, Texas Woman's University*

Mapping Multilingual Opportunities For Black Multilingual Youth Via Critical Race Spatial Analysis. *Reka C. Barton, University of Maryland; Malik Stevenson, California State University - Dominguez Hills; Aisha Haynes Young, Prepared To Teach/New York University*

22.061-8. Interrogating Perspectives and Practices in Bilingual Education (Table 8). SIG-Bilingual Education Research; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

How Are Emergent Bilinguals Supported? Insights from Observations of Business-as-Usual Social Studies Instruction. *Erin K. Hogan, University of Louisville; Leticia Martinez, University of Texas at Austin; Daniel Espinas,*

Vanderbilt University

Illusion of Choice: Immigrant Latine Caregivers Navigating Educational Decision-Making in New York City. *Emmeline Ortiz, New York City Department of Education*

Perceptions of bilingual education and bilingualism among parents and educators in the U.S. borderlands. *Christian E. Zuniga, University of Texas - Rio Grande Valley; GoMee Park, University of Texas - Rio Grande Valley*

Reframing Promotion: How Multilingual Learner Tenure and Proficiency Shape Secondary School Progression. *Simone Wilkinson, DC Public Schools*

Support or Segregation? Student Perspectives on the English Learner Label and English Language Development Classrooms. *Thaina Ferrari Deolindo, University of Arizona*

22.061-9. Navigating Student Well-Being in University Settings (Table 9). SIG-Stress, Coping, and Resilience; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Emerging Technologies for College Student Mental Health: Scoping Review Addressing Implementation Challenges and Future Directions. *Pearl Omolara Oladele, Washington State University; Deborah G. Fabiyi, Washington State University; Taiwo Feyijimi, University of Georgia; Olusola Olalekan Adesope, Washington State University*

Persistent Disparities in Mental Health Service Utilization Among First-Generation College Students: Evidence from the Healthy Minds Study, 2021–2024. *Stephanie Bobbitt, Monmouth University; Steven Michael Carlo, Monmouth University*

Reframing Stillness in STEM: First-Year Students' Experience with Mindfulness Practice to Cope with Stress. *Terrie Bradshaw, University of Central Florida; Steven Haberlin, University of Central Florida*

The Confidence to Cope: Building Well-Being Tools in a University Mindfulness Course. *Linda Yaron Weston, University of Southern California*

"Time to Thrive": Design and Evaluation of a Positive Psychology-Based Online Program to Foster Well-Being and Resilience Among University Students in Germany and the UK. *Ianina Scheuch, TU Dresden; Baerbel Fuerstenau, Dresden University of Technology; Gisele Dias, King's College London; Patricia Zunsain*

Chair: *Gal Harpaz, The Open University of Israel*

22.061-10. Financial Literacy and Numeracy Across Ecological Levels: Examining Global, National, Local, and Home Discourses of Financial Education (Table 10). SIG-

Research in Mathematics Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

From Symbols to Systems: Currency as a Tool for Global Citizenship Learning. *Rosalia Cha, University of Toronto - OISE; Emmanuelle LePichon-Vorstman, University of Toronto; Alexandre Cavalcante, University of Toronto*

Why should I trust this number? Re-mathematizing inflation in financial education. *Deborah Benhamu, University of Toronto - OISE; Annie Savard, McGill University; Alexandre Cavalcante, University of Toronto*

Financial numeracy education in informal settings: insights from designing a museum exhibition installation. *Andrew Jingyuan Li, University of Toronto - OISE; Mark Argo, Toronto Metropolitan University; Alexandre Cavalcante, University of Toronto*

Unschooling wealth: reimagining financial literacy through immigrant lived experience and currere. *Jin A Jung, University of Toronto - OISE; Molade Osibodu, York University; Alexandre Cavalcante, University of Toronto*

Fostering Equitable Math Learning Classrooms Through NICs: Middle School Students' Perspectives. *Pallavi Chhabra, Washington University in St. Louis; Jennifer Burris, University of Kentucky; Michelle M Wambua, Washington University in St. Louis; Rachel Ruggirello, Washington University in St. Louis; Alison Brockhouse, Washington University in St. Louis*

Chair: *Alexandre Cavalcante, University of Toronto*

Discussant: *Alexandre Cavalcante, University of Toronto*

22.062. AERA Roundtable Session Wednesday 11:45 am - Gold 3; Roundtable Session

22.062-1. Evolving Professional Roles and Identities in PE/PETE (Table 1). SIG-Research on Learning and Instruction in Physical Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Challenges of Co-creating a Physical Education Curriculum With Students: A Self study as a methodology. *Hyungsik Min, Arizona State University; Dong Liu, Arizona State University; Pamela H. Kulinna, Arizona State University; Donetta J. Cothran, Indiana University; Allison Poulos, Arizona State University*

Human Flourishing as the Main Idea of Models-Based Practice in School Physical Education. *Jamie Jacob Brunson, University of Memphis*

Teacher Support and Pre-service Physical Education Teacher Identity: Mediating Roles of Needs and Engagement.

Chenhao wu, 德克萨斯大学奥斯汀分校, Sizhe Liu, huaqiao m; Yongshun Wang, Huaqiao University; Xiaofen D. Hamilton, The university of Texas at Austin

The Impact of COVID-19 on PETE: Beginning Physical Education Teachers' Perception and Its Implications for Continuing Professional Development. *Baofu Wang, SUNY -*

College at Cortland; Xiaoping Fan, SUNY - College at Cortland; Xiaolu Liu, Georgia State University; Tanjian Liang, Central Washington University; Jingwen Liu, California State University - Fullerton; Yilin Li, California State University - Bakersfield

Providing continuous professional development for physical education teacher-led afterschool programs: A transtheoretical longitudinal investigation. *Victoria Shiver, University of New Mexico; Kelly L. Simonton, University of Wyoming; Jeanne M. Barcelona, Wayne State University; Michael Messerole, University of Nebraska - Omaha; Megan Lee, University of Wyoming; Erin Elizabeth Centeio, University of Hawai'i at Manoa*

Chair: *Seunghyun Baek, SUNY - College at Cortland*

22.062-2. Educators Navigating AI: Identity, Practice, and Pedagogy (Table 2). Division C - Learning and Instruction; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

An Analysis of Secondary Teachers' AI-Integrated Lessons Based on Activity Theory. *Jisoo Lee, Korea University; Hyojin Lee, Korea University; Innwoo Park, Korea University*

Examining Pre-service Teacher's Vision for AI Integration in Instructional Practice. *Yuxin Chen, University of South Alabama; Sohee Kim, University of South Alabama*

From Clicks to Criticality: Educator Knowledge for AI-Enhanced Literacy Learning. *Rebekah May Degener, Minnesota State University - Mankato; Beth Beschorner, Minnesota State University - Mankato*

Generative AI-Mediated Learning Trajectories: An Activity Theory Analysis of In-Service CS Educators' Engagement with ChatGPT. *Rui Tammy Huang, University of Florida; Ruohan Liu, Seattle University; John Hampton, University of Florida*

Mapping Cross-Disciplinary Collaboration in AI Curriculum: A Mixed-Methods Case Study of Teacher Learning in PD. *Qiuqing Li, North Carolina State University; Daria Smyslova, North Carolina State University; Amanda MacCormac, North Carolina State University; Shiyang Jiang, North Carolina State University*

Chair: *Panagiotis Kosmas, University of Limassol - Cyprus*

22.062-3. Immersive and Data-Rich STEM Learning Analytics (Table 3). Division C - Learning and Instruction; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Automatically Detecting Emotions during Game-based Learning using Large Language Models and Concurrent Verbal Protocols. *Elizabeth B. Cloude, Michigan State*

University; Trisha Reddy, University of Pennsylvania; Kieran Chetty, University of Pennsylvania; Qiyang Lin, Michigan State University; Li Zhang, Drexel University
Choosing the Future of Learning: Assessing Preferences for Educational GPTs through a Discrete Choice Experiment. *Belle Li, Purdue University; Yicheng Mao, Maastricht University*

Examining Spatial and Spatial Computational Thinking Outcomes in a Technology-Mediated STEM Context: Effects of Race, Gender, and Instructional Format. *Yan Sun, Mississippi State University; Timothy O Okunoye, Mississippi State University; Jamie Dyer, Mississippi State University*

Longitudinal Data Mining on Aspect-Based Sentiment with Behavioral Context in Game-based Coding of Autistic Learners. *Xiaoxue Zhou, University of Maryland; Fengfeng Ke, University of Maryland; Nuodi Zhang, Florida State University; Alex Barrett, Florida State University*

Sequencing Immersive Simulations for Cybersecurity: Task Complexity and Efficiency. *Taehyun Kim, Utah State University; Hyunju Oh, University of Florida; Mustafa Mohammad Shaky, University of Florida; Janise McNair, University of Florida; Rui Guo, University of Florida; Wanli Xing, University of Florida; Sandip Ray, University of Florida*

Chair: *Bo Pei, University of South Florida*

22.062-4. Teachers, Agency, and Systems: A Cultural-Historical Activity Theory Perspective (Table 4). SIG-Cultural-Historical Research; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Combining Sociocultural Perspectives on Teaching and Learning in Teacher Learning Communities. *Shaffiq N Welji, University of Georgia*

Cultural-Historical Activity Theory as a Framework for Teacher Support. *Taylor Beadles, University of Texas - Permian Basin*

Lactating Teachers' Bodily Needs and School Design: A Cultural-Historical Activity Theory Analysis. *Elise Toedt, University of Minnesota*

Unpacking the Dynamics of Utah's Dual Language Immersion Program: A Cultural-Historical Activity Theory Perspective. *Yamin Zheng, University of Rochester*

Chair: *Collin Perryman, Arizona State University*

Discussant: *Socorro Orozco, California State University - Los Angeles*

22.062-5. Roundtable: Higher Education and the Learning Sciences (Table 5). SIG-Learning Sciences; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Haptic Experiences Afford a Durable Understanding of Complex Systems. *Xiaoyu Tang, University of Iowa; Robb Lindgren, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Aishwari Talhan, University at Albany - SUNY; Matthew E. Lira, University of Iowa*

Planting Seeds for Pedagogical Change: Equity Conjectures for Organizational Learning in Academic Departments. *Reina Yorba-Rico, California State University - Monterey Bay; Karina Flores-Camacho, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Aida Arosoaie, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Aireale J. Rodgers, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Seductive Details in MOOCs: Distraction or Engagement? *Shrutii Mehta, University of Pennsylvania; Ryan S. Baker, University of Pennsylvania; Amanda Barany, University of Pennsylvania; Kirk Vanacore, University of Pennsylvania; J. M. Alexandra L. Andres, Learning Data Insights; Sameea Butt, New York University; Erin Chi, University of Pennsylvania*

The Emergent Architecture of a Theory-Informed Learning Sciences Program. *Jonan Phillip Donaldson, University of Alabama - Birmingham*

22.062-6. Culturally Relevant/Responsive and Critical Approaches to Reading and Literacy Education (Table 6). SIG-Research in Reading and Literacy; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

From Literary Societies to Read-Aloud Crates: A Historical Approach to Black Literacy Futures. *Brittany Powell, University of Delaware*

Histories of Resistance, Futures of Freedom: Black Male Literacy Practices as a Blueprint for Educational Transformation. *Mario Worlds, California State University - Fullerton*

Perception of Racism and Privilege Through the Lens of Korean American Adolescents. *Ji Hyun Hong, Emory University*

Reimagining Family Literacy Programs: Immigrant Mothers and Practitioners in Partnership. *Leigh Monistere, University of Pennsylvania; Jancarlos Montoya Mejia, University of Pennsylvania*

22.062-7. Young Children's Engagement in Culturally Relevant and Sustaining STEM (Table 7). SIG-Critical Perspectives on Early Childhood Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Critical Literacies for Critical Thinkers: STREAM Learning Rooted in Latinx Children's Cultural Realities. *Aura Yarenis*

Perez-Gonzalez, California State University - Long Beach; Mari Riojas-Cortez, California State University - Channel Islands

Early Childhood Under Threat: California Families Navigate Extreme Weather and Wildfires. *Fengrong Yang, Stanford University; WooJung Kim, Stanford University; Phil Fisher, Stanford University*

Who Is Allowed to Be Seen as a Scientist? Reimagining Representation and Educator Identity Through STEAM Picture Books. *Anne Valauri, Georgia Southern University*

Reimagining Participation: Black Children's Engagement in Early Computer Science Education through Culturally Relevant Interactions. *Charles E. Flowers, California State University - Fullerton; CRAFT Partnership, University of Tennessee*

Spatial Thinking with Children: Limits, Attachments, and Terrestrial Design for All the Living. *Laura Trafi-Prats, Manchester Metropolitan University*

Chair: *Ruby Batz, University of Nevada - Reno*

22.062-8. AI in Practice: Adoption and Reflection (Table 8).

SIG-Technology as an Agent of Change in Teaching and Learning; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

A Sociotechnical Systems Analysis of Arizona State University's Generative AI Strategy. *Yujie LI, Shanghai Jiao Tong University*

Developing Family Engagement Skills Through AI-Supported Reflective Practice. *Donna Wake, University of Central Arkansas; Steve Ward, University of Central Arkansas*

"Whenever using media, you should have purpose": A Study of Chinese Immigrant Parents' Media Practices. *Xiaoning Gui, University of North Texas; Daniel G. Krutka, University of North Texas*

Giving Voice Within a Voice: Rethinking Feedback and Assessment with GenAI. *Nadia Delanoy, University of Calgary; Danni Chen, Harbin Institute of Technology*

Chair: *Nicol R. Howard, Chapman University*

22.062-9. Rethinking Constructs and Measurement: Insights from Empirical Evidence (Table 9). Division H - Research, Evaluation and Assessment in Schools;

Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

A Multidimensional Framework for Assessing Adolescent Aesthetic Education: The IMPACT Model. *Ruiqi Li, Shanghai Jiao Tong University; Shuai Wang, Shanghai Jiao Tong University; Xin Gao, Shanghai Jiao Tong University; Mingxin An, University of Amsterdam; Miao Yang, Tsinghua University; Qiang Zhao, Northeast Normal University*

Measurement Invariance of the Curiosity Scale Across School Types in South America: PISA 2022 Evidence. *Solange Barros, University of Kansas*

Conditional Process Modeling of Experience and Background on Skills and Adherence to Test Construction Principles. *Francis Ankomah, Ohio University; Frank A Oppong, Ohio University; Regina Nugba, University of Cape Coast; Salima Jallow, Ohio University*

The changing relationship between post-secondary outcomes, standardized test performance and state college-readiness standards. *Toni Templeton, University of Houston; Willa Friedman, University of Houston; Catherine L. Horn, University of Houston*

Chair: *Justice Dadzie, University of Alabama*

22.062-10. School-Based Mental Health and Restorative Practices for Student Success (Table 10). Division H -

Research, Evaluation and Assessment in Schools;
Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Improving PreK-12 Student Outcomes Through School-Based Mental Health: Evidence from a Quasi-Experimental Study. *Elizabeth L. Adams, American Institutes for Research; Maria Dracopoli, American Institutes for Research; Matthew J. Farmer, American Institutes for Research; Marc C. Sanders, Milwaukee Public Schools; Travis Pinter, Milwaukee Public Schools; Rachel Chamberlain, American Institutes for Research*

A School Mental Health Research-Practice Partnership: Implementation of a Tier 2 Intervention. *Katie Eklund, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Stephen Kilgus, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Andy Garbacz, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Kierin Barnett, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Teachers' Perceptions of the Implementation of Restorative Practices. *Alexis Leon, Azusa Pacific University; Ying Hong Jiang, Azusa Pacific University*

Chair: *Catherine P. Bradshaw, University of Virginia*

Division and SIG Posters

22.063. AERA Poster Session Wednesday 11:45am; Poster Session

22.063-1. Poster Session I -- AERA Division D Section 1: Measurement, Psychometrics, and Assessment. Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Poster Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Posters:

1. AI Literacy Proxy from PISA 2022 Hong Kong: IRT and SEM Validation with ICT Capabilities (Poster 1). *Linwei Yu, The University of Hong Kong; Yueru Li, University of Macau*
2. A New Automatic Content Scoring based on Knowledge Graph for Constructed-Response Item (Poster 2). *Canxi Cao, University of International Relations; Liping Yang, Beijing Institute of Educational Supervision and Evaluation; Tao Xin, Beijing Normal University*
3. CAT and Item Misfit: Robustness, Consequences, and Practical Guidance (Poster 3). *Beyza Aksu-Dunya, Bartin University; Stefanie A. Wind, University of Alabama*
4. From Classical to Contemporary: A Psychometric Reanalysis of the DANVA-2-RV Using IRT Models (Poster 4). *Alessandro De Santis, University of Foggia; Silvia Capodivacca, Università Telematica Pegaso; Giusi Antonia Toto, University of Foggia; Pierpaolo Limone, Università Telematica Pegaso*
5. Imagining the Future of AI Literacy: Leveraging Theory Toward Principled Design of LLM-Enabled Scenario-Based Assessments (Poster 5). *Jesse R. Sparks, Educational Testing Service; Caitlin Tenison, ETS; Teresa M. Ober, Educational Testing Service; Tenaha P. O'Reilly, Educational Testing Service*
6. Testing the Waters: Using Test Theory to Create the [REDACTED] Survey Instrument (Poster 6). *Ella Claire Walsh, Boston College; Laura M. O'Dwyer, Boston College; Victoria Centurino, Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution; Nicholas Bates, Arizona State University - Bermuda Institute of Ocean Sciences; Sonya Dyhrman, Columbia University; Sheean Haley, Columbia University*
7. A Study of Measurement Invariance in Math Anxiety and Self-Efficacy Scales (Poster 7). *Alicia Jane Peras, University of Arizona; Nicholas Bishop, University of Arizona*
8. Bayesian Multidimensional Models Fit to Comparative Judgment Data on Art Educator Perceptions of Art Ability (Poster 8). *Steven Heil, Indiana University*
9. Measurement Invariance of Media Literacy Between Young Adults and Older Adults in South Korea (Poster 9). *Eunho Jo, Yonsei University; Stella Yun Kim, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Hyoun K. Kim, Yonsei University*
10. Psychometric Properties of the Adolescent and Adult Time Inventory-Turkish: Evidence From Gifted and Talented Adolescents (Poster 10). *Raymond Quang Vo, University of California - Berkeley; Ilke Bayazitli, University of California - Berkeley; Hetvi Desai, University of California - Berkeley; Ekene Azuka, University of California - Berkeley; Linsey B. Cohen, University of California - Berkeley; Golzar Ejadi, University of California - Berkeley; Emely Natali Lugo, University of California - Berkeley; Carlos Isaac Rivera, University of California - Berkeley; Kayla C. Thomas, University of California - Berkeley*
11. Facial Orientations and Head Movements Comparison in Different Scaffolding Strategies during Shared Book

Reading (Poster 11). *Boyuan LIU, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Si Chen, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Xuerong Wang, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Xiao Xiao, Fudan University; Yujia Chen, Fudan University*

12. Dimensional Structure and Cross-Cultural Measurement Invariance of a Self-Esteem Scale Using Multidimensional IRT (Poster 12). *Talal Alzabidi, University of North Carolina Greensboro; Reben Ramadhan Ramadhan Saleh, Lobachevsky State University*

22.063-2. Div J, Section 4 Poster Session 1. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Posters:

13. Beyond Active Learning: Instructor Practices Connected to Students' Sense of Belonging in Introductory STEM Courses (Poster 13). *Yoon Ha Choi, Digital Promise; Taylor Alexander, Digital Promise; Julie Neisler, Digital Promise*
14. Effectiveness of a First-Year Course Design Resulting in Narrowing Learning Gaps (Poster 14). *Deborah M. Oh, California State University, Los Angeles; Joshua M. Kim, California State University - Los Angeles; Nazgol Makki, California State University - Los Angeles; Zhengqing Ni, California State University - Los Angeles; Wonjoo Shepard, California State University - Los Angeles*
15. Evaluating the Impact of an Active Learning Institute on Student Success (Poster 15). *Kameryn Denaro, University of California - Irvine; Jeffrey M. DeVries, University of California - Irvine; Richard B. Arum, University of California - Irvine*
16. Exploring Belonging and Cultural Competence Among Women of Color in Introductory STEM at HSI-Community College (Poster 16). *Elizabeth Nguyen, San Diego State University*
17. Exploring the Theoretical Foundations of an iSTEM Graduate Program using Epistemic Network Analysis (Poster 17). *Cynthia Esperanza Lima, University of Texas - San Antonio; Guadalupe Carmona, University of Texas - San Antonio; Veronica Vargas-Alejo, Universidad de Guadalajara; Saugata Datta, University of Texas - San Antonio; Harshad Kulkarni, Indian Institute of Technology Mandi; Luis E. Montero Moguel, University of Texas - San Antonio*
18. Faculty Perceptions of Higher Education Quality in Afghanistan (2022-2024) (Poster 18). *Sayed Nasratullah Mussawy, University of Massachusetts - Amherst*
19. Faculty Teaching and Research Productivity and Equity in STEM: Student Grade Gaps in Lower-Division Courses (Poster 19). *Anna Kye, University of California - Irvine; Brian Sato, University of California - Irvine; Kameryn Denaro, University of California - Irvine*
20. Humanizing Online STEM: The Impact of Professional Development on Instructor Beliefs and Student Outcomes

(Poster 20). *Gala Merari Ledezma, University of California - Irvine; Di Xu, University of California - Irvine; Michelle Pacansky-Brock, Foothill College; Kimberly Vincent-Layton, Cal Poly Humboldt University*

21. Improving Student Success through Faculty Development: Evidence from Gateway Courses at a Public HBCU (Poster 21). *Paloma Benavides, ACUE; Elizabeth K. Lawner, Association of College and University Educators; Meghan Snow, Association of College and University Educators*
22. Improving Teaching Effectiveness in a TESL Collaborative Program: Insights from Student Feedback (Poster 22). *Shuxiong Feng, University of Delaware; Fan Zhang, University of Delaware*
23. Institutional Drivers and State Contexts: Examining Variation in Community College Faculty Support Expenditures (Poster 23). *Xiwei Zhu, San Diego State University*
24. Mind the Gap: Understanding and Predicting Education Inequity in Undergraduate STEM Active Learning Courses (Poster 24). *Shangmou Xu, University of Washington; Annie Colgan, University of Washington; Sarah L. Eddy, University of Minnesota; Elli Theobald, University of Washington*
25. Optimizing Corequisite Support Design: Instructional and Implementation Features Predicting Success in Gateway English and Math (Poster 25). *Hongjiao Li, University of California - Irvine; XunFei Li, University of California - Irvine; Di Xu, University of California - Irvine*

22.063-3. ATL Poster Session 1: AI Integration and Student Outcomes in K-12 Settings. SIG-Advanced Technologies for Learning; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Posters:

26. A Systematic Review of Artificial Intelligence in K-12 Science Education : Themes, Effectiveness, and Challenges (Poster 26). *Haifeng Wu, East China Normal University*
27. Co-Thinking with Artificial Intelligence: Exploring Critical Thinking Through Ill-Structured Problems (Poster 27). *Ibrahim Akdilek, Texas Tech University; Merve Basdogan, Texas Tech University*
28. Fairness vs. Overcorrection: Investigating Input Effects in AI-Powered Writing Assessment (Poster 28). *Ghaida S. Alrawashdeh, Oakland University*
29. Generative AI in Education: A Meta-Analysis of its Impact on Student Achievement (Poster 29). *Xiuxiu Tang, University of Notre Dame; Liu Dong, Purdue University; Xiyu Wang, Purdue University; Jingxian Cecilia Zhang, Mount St. Mary's University*
30. Multimodal Participation Analysis in CSCL Through AI-Enhanced Activity Mapping and Screen Recording Video Analysis Systems (Poster 30). *Hakeoung Hannah Lee, University of Virginia; Miguel E Lujan, University of New*

Mexico; Venkatesh Jatla, Virginia Tech Carilion; Ugesh Egala, Independent Scholar; Marios S. Pattichis, University of New Mexico; Sylvia Celedon-Pattichis, University of Texas at Austin; Esteban Cantu, University of Texas at Austin

31. Scalable Human–AI Workflow for Middle School Math Question Creation (Poster 31). *Hai Li, University of Florida; Rui Guo, University of Florida; Chenglu Li, University of Utah; Wanli Xing, University of Florida*
32. The Efficacy of Generative AI on Students’ Performance in K-12 and Higher Education: A Meta-Analysis (Poster 32). *Hye K. Pae, University of Cincinnati; Hanzhong Sun, University of Cincinnati; Detong Xia, Xi’an Jiaotong-Liverpool University; Gulbahar H. Beckett, Iowa State University*

22.063-4. Pursuing Equitable and Inclusionary Access in the K-12 Pipeline. SIG-Urban Learning, Teaching, and Research; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Posters:

33. Futuring Equity: How mentorship increases the self-efficacy of novice Black male teachers in racialized schools (Poster 33). *Ronald Drummond, Bowie State University*
34. Problematizing “Nice”: The NICCE Framework for Cultivating Critical Consciousness in Teacher Education (Poster 34). *Christopher Lee Harris, Duquesne University; Jennifer L. Martin, University of Illinois at Springfield*

22.063-5. Tracked and Displaced: Gentrification, Latinx Mathematics Achievement, and Structural Educational Inequality. SIG-Latina/o/x Research Issues; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Poster:

35. Tracked and Displaced: Gentrification, Latinx Mathematics Achievement, and Structural Educational Inequality (Poster 35). *Elizabeth I. Rivera, Montclair State University*

22.063-6. Innovations in Higher Education Assessment and Measurement. SIG-Measurement and Assessment in Higher Education; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Posters:

36. Assessment Data Use and Pedagogical Innovation in Higher Education. A Meta-synthesis (Poster 36). *Serafina Pastore, University of Bari*
37. Model Selection in Educational Assessment: Cognitive Diagnosis vs. Item Response Theory in a Medical Education Case Study (Poster 37). *Youn Seon Lim, University of Cincinnati; Nicholas Burkhart, University of Cincinnati*

22.063-7. General Linear Modeling in Regression Discontinuity Designs. SIG-Multiple Linear Regression: The General Linear Model; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Posters:

38. What We Learned About Power Calculations for Regression Discontinuity Designs: The eMERGE study (Poster 38). *T. Mark Beasley, University of Alabama - Birmingham*
39. The Influence of Parental Education on Offspring Earnings: Empirical Analysis Using CFPS2014-2020 Data (Poster 39). *Tianyi Sun, East China Normal University; Chunshun Yan, East China Normal University*

22.063-8. Qualitative Research SIG Poster Session. SIG-Qualitative Research; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Poster:

40. Examining Reciprocity from Different Educational Stakeholder Groups: Photo Perspectives (Poster 40). *Cynthia C. Reyes, University of Vermont; Sonya Sachar, University of Alberta; Arby Mohamed Ghemari, University of Vermont*

22.063-9. Title IX Coordinators and Upholding Gender Equity. SIG-Research on Women and Education; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Poster:

41. Upholding Gender Equity: Title IX Coordinators’ Experiences Supporting Pregnant and Parenting Postsecondary Students (Poster 41). *Lori D. Rhea, University of Houston*

22.063-10. SIG Socio Political Issues in Mathematics and Science Education Poster Session. SIG-Socio-Political Issues in Mathematics and Science Education; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Posters:

42. AI as Archeological Evidence: Uncovering Dominant Teaching Discourse in Educational Technology (Poster 42). *Cindy Yovanov, Drexel University; Amanda Reinsburrow, Drexel University; Jason Silverman, Drexel University*
43. Equity Without Excellence? Rethinking Mathematical Literacy in Indonesia After PISA 2022 (Poster 43). *Anis Munfarikhatin, Syracuse University*

22.063-11. Measuring What Matters: Validating Constructs of Readiness and Global Competence. SIG-Test Validity

Research and Evaluation; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall -
Exhibit Hall A; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Poster:

44. Fewer Questions, Sharper Insights: Measuring College Preparedness Using Item Response Theory (Poster 44). *Holden Tibbetts Ellis, University of California - Santa Barbara; Travis Rodolfo Candieas, University of California - Santa Barbara*

22.063-12. Division I - Education in the Professions Poster Session. Division I - Education in the Professions; Poster Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall -
Exhibit Hall A; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Posters:

45. Designing Immersive VR Learning for Healthcare: A Mixed-Methods Evaluation of the V+Care Simulation (Poster 45). *Leonie Kopahs, University of Goettingen; Matthias Schumann, University of Goettingen*
46. Digital Resource Utilization Environments and Digital Literacy among Chinese Engineering Students (Poster 46). *ao shen, Tianjin University; Xinqiao Liu, Tianjin University*

22.064. e-Lightning Ed-Talk Session 3 - Stage 1. AERA e-

Lightning Ed-Talks; AERA Ed Talk
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Exhibit Hall A
- Stage 1; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Psychometric Properties of the Adolescent and Adult Time Inventory—Turkish: Evidence From Gifted and Talented Adolescents (Stage 1, 11:50 AM). *Raymond Quang Vo, University of California - Berkeley; Ilke Bayazitli, University of California - Berkeley; Hetvi Desai, University of California - Berkeley; Ekene Azuka, University of California - Berkeley; Linsey B. Cohen, University of California - Berkeley; Golzar Ejadi, University of California - Berkeley; Emely Natali Lugo, University of California - Berkeley; Carlos Isaac Rivera, University of California - Berkeley; Kayla C. Thomas, University of California - Berkeley*

Measurement Invariance of Media Literacy Between Young Adults and Older Adults in South Korea (Stage 1, 11:59 AM). *Eunho Jo, Yonsei University; Stella Yun Kim, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Hyoun K. Kim, Yonsei University*

A Study of Measurement Invariance in Math Anxiety and Self-Efficacy Scales (Stage 1, 12:08 PM). *Alicia Jane Peras, University of Arizona; Nicholas Bishop, University of Arizona*

Imagining the Future of AI Literacy: Leveraging Theory Toward Principled Design of LLM-Enabled Scenario-Based Assessments (Stage 1, 12:17 PM). *Jesse R. Sparks, Educational Testing Service; Caitlin Tenison, ETS; Teresa M. Ober, Educational Testing Service; Tenaha P. O'Reilly,*

Educational Testing Service

Dimensional Structure and Cross-Cultural Measurement Invariance of a Self-Esteem Scale Using Multidimensional IRT (Stage 1, 12:26 PM). *Talal Alzabidi, University of North Carolina Greensboro; Reben Ramadhan Ramadhan Saleh, Lobachevsky State University*

The Efficacy of Generative AI on Students' Performance in K-12 and Higher Education: A Meta-Analysis (Stage 1, 12:35 PM). *Hye K. Pae, University of Cincinnati; Hanzhong Sun, University of Cincinnati; Detong Xia, Xi'an Jiaotong-Liverpool University; Gulbahar H. Beckett, Iowa State University*

Co-Thinking with Artificial Intelligence: Exploring Critical Thinking Through Ill-Structured Problems (Stage 1, 12:44 PM). *Ibrahim Akdilek, Texas Tech University; Merve Basdogan, Texas Tech University*

AI as Archeological Evidence: Uncovering Dominant Teaching Discourse in Educational Technology (Stage 1, 12:53 PM). *Cindy Yovanov, Drexel University; Amanda Reinsburrow, Drexel University; Jason Silverman, Drexel University*

Equity Without Excellence? Rethinking Mathematical Literacy in Indonesia After PISA 2022 (Stage 1, 1:02 PM). *Anis Munfarikhatin, Syracuse University*

Chair: *Laura S. Hamilton, National Center for the Improvement of Educational Assessment, Inc.*

22.065. e-Lightning Ed-Talk Session 3 - Stage 2. AERA e-

Lightning Ed-Talks; AERA Ed Talk
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Exhibit Hall A
- Stage 2; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Effectiveness of a First-Year Course Design Resulting in Narrowing Learning Gaps (Stage 2, 11:50 AM). *Deborah M. Oh, California State University, Los Angeles; Joshua M. Kim, California State University - Los Angeles; Nazgol Makki, California State University - Los Angeles; Zhengqing Ni, California State University - Los Angeles; Wonjoo Shepard, California State University - Los Angeles*

Evaluating the Impact of an Active Learning Institute on Student Success (Stage 2, 11:59 AM). *Kameryn Denaro, University of California - Irvine; Jeffrey M. DeVries, University of California - Irvine; Richard B. Arum, University of California - Irvine*

Exploring Belonging and Cultural Competence Among Women of Color in Introductory STEM at HSI-Community College (Stage 2, 12:08 PM). *Elizabeth Nguyen, San Diego State University*

Faculty Teaching and Research Productivity and Equity in STEM: Student Grade Gaps in Lower-Division Courses (Stage 2, 12:17 PM). *Anna Kye, University of California - Irvine; Brian Sato, University of California - Irvine; Kameryn Denaro, University of California - Irvine*

Institutional Drivers and State Contexts: Examining Variation in Community College Faculty Support Expenditures (Stage

2, 12:26 PM). *Xiwei Zhu, San Diego State University*
 Mind the Gap: Understanding and Predicting Education
 Inequity in Undergraduate STEM Active Learning Courses
 (Stage 2, 12:35 PM). *Shangmou Xu, University of
 Washington; Annie Colgan, University of Washington; Sarah
 L. Eddy, University of Minnesota; Elli Theobald, University
 of Washington*
 Upholding Gender Equity: Title IX Coordinators' Experiences
 Supporting Pregnant and Parenting Postsecondary Students
 (Stage 2, 12:44 PM). *Lori D. Rhea, University of Houston*
 Problematizing "Nice": The NICCE Framework for Cultivating
 Critical Consciousness in Teacher Education (Stage 2, 12:53
 PM). *Christopher Lee Harris, Duquesne University; Jennifer
 L. Martin, University of Illinois at Springfield*
 Chair: *LaWanda W. Ward, Pennsylvania State University*

University
 Instructors: *Dina Naji Arch, University of California - Santa
 Barbara; Marsha M. Ing, University of California -
 Riverside*

**24.012. PD26-09 Navigating Sex and Gender in Educational
 Research: A Guide to Inclusive Language and Data
 Collection.** Professional Development and Training
 Committee; Professional Development Course
 JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Plaza III;
 12:45-4:45pm
 Instructors: *Kaley Mumma, Purdue University; Tiffany A.
 Marzolino, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign;
 Neil A. Knobloch, Purdue University*

Wednesday, April 8th, 12:00 pm

AERA Related Activities

**23.010. AERA Undergraduate Student Workshop - Day 1
 (Invitation Only).** AERA Related Activities; Workshop
 Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 505;
 12:00-6:00pm
 Chair: *George L. Wimberly, American Educational Research
 Association*

Wednesday, April 8th, 12:45 pm

Professional Development Courses

**24.010. PD26-07 Using the Interview Quality Reflection Tool
 (IQR) to Hone the Craft of Interviewing.** Professional
 Development and Training Committee; Professional
 Development Course
 JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Plaza I;
 12:45-4:45pm
 Director: *James L Huff, University of Georgia*
 Instructors: *James L Huff, University of Georgia; Jerrod
 Henderson, University of Houston; Sindia M. Rivera-
 Jiménez, University of Florida*

**24.011. PD26-08 The Utility of Mixture Modeling In
 Educational Research.** Professional Development and
 Training Committee; Professional Development Course
 JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Plaza II;
 12:45-4:45pm
 Directors: *Karen L. Nylund-Gibson, University of California -
 Santa Barbara; Katherine E. Masyn, Georgia State*

Wednesday, April 8th, 1:45 pm

Presidential Sessions

**25.010. Disability Justice in (Special) Education Futures:
 Exploring Critical, Intersectional, and Social and
 Emotional Dimensions.** AERA Presidential Session;
 Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 406AB;
 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Advancing the Social and Emotional Inclusion of Students with
 Disabilities: From Discourse to Measurement and Practices.
*Christina Cipriano, Yale University; Michael McCarthy,
 Yale Child Study Center*
 Re-Framing the Master Narratives of Learning Dis/Abilities
 through an Emotion and Intersectional Lens. *David I.
 Hernandez-Saca, University of Northern Iowa*
 Learning for Dis/abled Bilingual Latina/o/x Youth: Expanding
 to the Consequential for Transformative Futures. *Taucia
 Gonzalez, University of Arizona; Joan J. Hong, University of
 Maryland; Mariana Pacheco, University of Wisconsin -
 Madison; Kate Roberts, University of Wisconsin - Madison;
 Na Lor, Teachers College, Columbia University*
 Intersectional Consciousness: Transnational Lessons on
 Disability Justice. *Mildred Boveda, Pennsylvania State
 University*

Chair: *Patrick Camangian, University of San Francisco*
 Discussant: *Kaleb Germinaro, University of Illinois at Chicago*

**25.011. In the Hour of Chaos: Hip Hop Art and Activism with
 Public Enemy's Chuck D.** AERA Presidential Session;
 Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 403A;

1:45-3:15pm

Chair: *H. Samy Alim, University of California - Los Angeles*
Panelists: *Chuck D, Public Enemy; Gloria J. Ladson-Billings, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Robin D. G. Kelley, University of California - Los Angeles; Lauren Leigh Kelly, Rutgers University; Tabia N. Shawel, University of California - Los Angeles*

AERA Research and Science Policy Sessions

25.012. Data and Computing in K–12 Education: Foundational Competencies – A Report from the National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine. AERA Science and Policy Sessions; Invited Speaker Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 404AB;
1:45-3:15pm

Chair: *Christopher J. Dede, Harvard University*
Participants: *Victor R. Lee, Stanford University; Andee Rubin, TERC; Joshua Rosenberg, University of Tennessee; Shuchi Grover, Looking Glass Ventures*
Discussants: *Mimi M. Recker, Utah State University; Thomas M. Philip, University of California - Berkeley*

AERA Sessions

25.013. Navigating Difficult Conversations: Conflict Resolution Strategies for the AERA Community. AERA Sessions; Workshop
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 501B;
1:45-3:15pm
Participants: *Shannon Lynn Burton, Michigan State University; Kamaria B. Porter, Northwestern University*

25.014. Storying Our Black Student Achievement in Los Angeles Schools. Spotlight on Los Angeles and the Region; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 403B;
1:45-3:15pm

Chair: *Sonya Douglass, Teachers College, Columbia University*
Participants: *Traci Ausby, California State University - Long Beach; Paige Desmore, LAUSD Black Student Achievement Program Coordinator; Tamisha Donald, California State University Dominguez Hills; Gloria Page, California State University Dominguez Hills*
Discussant: *Priya Goel, California State University - Dominguez Hills*

Committee Sessions

25.015. Critical Epistemologies and Methodologies:

Reclaiming Knowledge, Story, and Belonging Across Educational Spaces. Committee on Scholars of Color in Education; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 409AB;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Beyond the White Space: Racialized Barriers and Transformative Potential in Critical Quantitative Research. Ebony O. McGee, Johns Hopkins University; Odis Johnson, Johns Hopkins University; Darnell Leatherwood, University of Michigan; Diondraya Taylor, University of California - Los Angeles; Zariah Nicole, Johns Hopkins University
Carrying Stories Forward: Deepening Our Places and Spaces Through Collectivity Across Institutions and Communities. Leola Paquin, University of New Mexico; Danielle R. Lansing, Southwestern Indian Polytechnic Institute
Conceptualizations of Knowledge and Its Influence on Sense of Belonging among BBIWOC Scholars. Bethany Parker, University of Tennessee
Endarkened Alchemy as Ancestral Listening, Spiritual Co-Writing, and Educational Liberation. Kiese Vita, California State University - East Bay
Towards Black Women's Embodiment of Liberatory Emotional Justice in the Academy. Renée Wilmot, Michigan State University; Dorinda Carter Andrews, Michigan State University

Chair: *Noor Ali, Northeastern University*

Discussant: *James Wright, Temple University*

25.016. Division B Fireside Chat: Rooted Futures: Race, Gender, and Technology as Curricular Tools of Resistance. Graduate Student Council; Invited Speaker Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 402A;
1:45-3:15pm

Chairs: *Emmanuel J. Watkins, University of Alabama; Curtis O'Dwyer, University of Wisconsin - Madison*
Panelists: *Leah Tonnelle Gaines, University of Central Florida; Wilson Kwamogi Okello, Pennsylvania State University; Bernadette Baker, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

25.017. Indigenous Perspectives on Knowledge that Colonialism Tries to Forget and Indigenous Peoples Seek to Remember. International Relations Committee; Invited Speaker Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 511C;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Ngā Hanganga Matua o te Whakaako Hitori: Critiquing the Aotearoa New Zealand Histories Curriculum Reset. Nēpia Mahuika, Massey University; Richard Francis Manning, University of Canterbury
Precarity and Stepping Stones to Indigenous Futures. Nikki Moodie, University of Melbourne

Dreaming Futures, Remembering Histories: Sámi Teachers' Visions for Land-Based Curriculum Renewal. *Ylva Jannok Nutti, Sami University of Applied Sciences; Rauna Rahko-Ravanti, Sámi University of Applied Sciences; Berit-Ellen Juuso, Sami University of Applied Sciences*

Reimagining Futures Through the Lens of Indigenous Food Sovereignty and Knowledge Systems. *Mariaelena Huambachano, Syracuse University*

Chair: *Linda T. Smith, Te Whare Wananga o Awanuiarangi*

Discussants: *Megan Bang, Northwestern University; Stephanie Fryberg, Northwestern University*

25.018. Surviving Disruption: A Cross-generational Dialogue on the Impact of Federal Legislation on Student Futures. Social Justice Action Committee; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 501C;
1:45-3:15pm

Chair: *Denise M. Taliaferro Baszile, Wayne State University*

Participants: *Dawn G. Williams, Howard University; Kimberly A. White-Smith, University of San Diego; Antwuan Williams, Wayne State University; Stephen D. Hancock, North Carolina A&T State University*

International Organization Sessions

25.019. Constructing a New Vision for Educational Leadership in Challenging Times. International Aligned Organizations/Commonwealth Council for Educational Administration and Management - CCEAM; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum A; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

A New Paradigm for Educational Leadership. *Carolyn M. Shields, Wayne State University*

What do notions of decolonizing educational leadership offer educational leaders towards transformative, equitable and socially just practice. *Ann E. Lopez, University of Toronto - OISE*

The will and the skills: Leaders overcoming disparities by bridging policy expectations with a critically informed model for change. *Mere Berryman, University of Waikato*

Sense making, storytelling and futures thinking as essential tools for social justice leadership. *David M. Gurr, University of Melbourne; Christopher Hudson, Westbourne Grammar School; Nada Jarni, RMIT University*

Education Leadership grounded in the power of our shared humanity to preserve and strengthen liberal democracy. *Margaret Grogan, Chapman University*

Leading for Justice in Early Years Transitions: Relational Praxis and Policy Enactment in a Small-State System. *Heathcliff Schembri, Malta College of Arts, Science and Technology (MCAST); Eliza Cachia, Malta College of Arts, Science and Technology*

Chair: *Carolyn M. Shields, Wayne State University*

Division Sessions

25.020. Principal Labor Market Outcomes: Capturing the Influences of Race, Place, and School Climate. Division A - Administration; Paper Session

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Los Feliz; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Principal race and the racialized contexts of schools: A systematic review. *Thomas Michael Drake, University of Michigan; LI LIU, University of Michigan; Huihui Chen, University of Michigan; Ruijie Zhao, University of Michigan; Bangju Luo, Michigan State University; Aofan Wang, University of Michigan; Ya Li, University of Michigan*

School Climate and Principal Turnover: Do Principals Stay Where the Climate Is Strong? Evidence from Georgia Schools. *Bakhyt Zhumatay, Michigan State University; Jerome Graham, Michigan State University*

The Racial and Gendered Dimensions of Principal Demotion: A 1999–2017 Analysis of Texas Schools. *Lauren P. Bailes, University of Delaware; Sarah Guthery, University of Oklahoma*

Who Stays, Who Leaves? A National Survival Analysis of Chile's School Principals. *Christian Lazcano, Universidad del Desarrollo; Soledad Ortuzar, Universidad del Desarrollo; Sara Galilea, Universidad del Desarrollo; Pablo Siegel, Universidad del Desarrollo; Maria Paz Arriagada, Universidad del Desarrollo*

Chair: *Huang Wu, University of Missouri - Kansas City*

Discussant: *Melody May Yin Isabela, Claremont Graduate University*

25.021. Social-Emotional Dimensions of Leadership. Division A - Administration; Paper Session

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Los Cerritos; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

The Emotional Parts of Leadership: The Wounded Educational Leader Making Meaning, Processing, Healing and Recovery. *Rafaela Espinal, Teachers College*

Reimagining Trauma-Informed Leadership: Transformative Futures in Educational Crisis Management. *Jennifer Charteris, University of New England - Australia; Adele Nye, University of New England - Australia; sarah Oluk, University of New England, Australia*

What You Can't Do Is Waffle: Women in School Leadership During COVID-19. *Courtney Beth Cavellier, University of St. Thomas (MN)*

Voices from the Top: District Leaders' Perspectives on Occupational Wellbeing. *Seijoon Park, National Institute of Education, Nanyang Technological University, Singapore;*

Laura K. Rogers, University of Virginia; Rachel Sue White, University of Texas at Austin

School Leadership Reflections: How Memories (Positive or Negative) Impact the Present. *Victor Alberto Ruiz-Divas, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Osly J. Flores, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Chair: *Natasha N. Johnson, Augusta University*

Discussant: *Vajra M. Watson, University of Redlands*

25.022. From Digital Textbooks to YouTube: Innovations in Digital Learning Design. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Paper Session

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, San Bernardino; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

AI Multi-Agent Enhanced Online Learning Communities: An Analysis of Collective Knowledge Construction. *Xiaojie Niu, Shandong University; Jingjing Zhang, Beijing Normal University*

Do Digital Textbooks Enhance K-12 Students' Learning Attitudes? Evidence from a Meta-Analysis. *Longyue Fang, East China Normal University; Hao Lei, East China Normal University; Chunming Yang, East China Normal University; Mingchen Wei, East China Normal University*

Evaluating Students' Experiences and Perceptions of a Digitalized Simulated Environment in a Distance Learning Program in Special and Inclusive Education. *Nikleia Eteokleous, Frederick University; Raphaela Neophytou, Frederick University; Olga Lyra, Frederick University*

Mind the Digital Gap: Genre and Instructional Supports in Children's Informational YouTube Videos. *Wei Pu, University of Hong Kong; Somin Park, The University of Hong Kong; Rebecca Dore, University of Delaware; James Alex Bonus, The Ohio State University; Brenna Hassinger-Das, Pace University*

Revising Online Textbooks with Multimedia Design Principles Improves Retention Learning. *Dharma Lewis, University of California - Santa Barbara; Richard E. Mayer, University of California - Santa Barbara*

Chair: *Rudy Silva Mera, EDITH Foundation*

25.023. Immersive Learning Environments. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Paper Session

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, La Cienega; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Augmented Storying: Forest Entanglements and More-than-Human Narratives in Children's AR Stories. *Kristiina Kumpulainen, University of British Columbia; Shima Dadkhahfard, University of Calgary; Harini Rajagopal, University of British Columbia; Melanie Wong, University of British Columbia; Jennifer A. Vadeboncoeur, University of British Columbia; Anne Michelle Burke, Memorial University*

Constructing Complex Learning Environment Towards Developing Industrial Robot Technicians' Skills Using Design-based Research. *Dang Bofei, Tianjin University; Sun Nan, East China Normal University; Haoming Wang, East China Normal University*

Educational Escape Rooms Instead of Clinical Simulations for Nursing Students? *Chaewon Kim, Florida State University; Brooke Evans, Florida State University; Lana Lipscomb, Florida State University; Tammy Paarlberg, Florida State University*

The Impact of Emotional and Achromatic Visual Design on Cognitive Load and Learning Outcome in Multimedia Learning. *Joshua Oghenefoego Okor, Washington State University; Oluwafemi J. Sunday, Washington State University; Chloe G. Dydasco, Washington State University; Olusola Olalekan Adesope, Washington State University*

Tools, Materials, and Practices: Examining Social Infrastructure in Maker Classrooms. *Andreina Yulis San Juan, Simon Fraser University; Zi Lin, Simon Fraser University; Yumiko Murai, Simon Fraser University*

Chair: *Gayathri Sadanala, Truman State University*

25.024. Promoting Cognitive and Contextual Agency Through Scalable Interventions for Self-Regulated Learning and Adaptive Performance. Division C - Learning and Instruction Cosponsored with SIG-Studying and Self-Regulated Learning; Symposium

Westin Bonaventure, Level 2, Mt. Washington; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Promoting Self-Regulated Learning in Higher Education with Digital Training: An RCT with Interviews. *Olav Schewe, University of Oxford*

Investigating Delivery Schedules for Scalable Learning Skill Training in Early Undergraduate Active Learning STEM Courses. *Matthew L. Bernacki, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Jenifer Utz, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Christy Strong, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Kathryn Rafferty, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*

Effects of Personalizing Science of Learning Instruction to Dual Enrollment High School Students' Prior Knowledge. *Shelbi Laura Kuhlmann, University of Memphis; C. Noelle Patterson, University of Memphis; Haley Siegfried, University of Memphis; Christina Hollander-Blackmon, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Sarayu Satyasai Yenumula, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Matthew L. Bernacki, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*

From Reaction to Regulation: Leveraging Contextualized Agency to Manage Amygdala Hijack. *Judy (Jiayun) He, Stanford University; Tina A. Grozter, Harvard University; Megan Powell Cuzzolino, Harvard University; Yu Hao, University of Oxford; Olav Schewe, University of Oxford*

Chair: *Olav Schewe, University of Oxford*

Discussant: *Rayne A. Sperling, Pennsylvania State University*

25.025. Reimagining Youth Agency: Pedagogies of Voice, Power, and Possibility. Division E - Counseling and Human Development; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 301B;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

There's a Long Line of Hands Carrying Your Name: Black school counselors and (Re)storying K-12 Schools for Black youth. *Renae D. Mayes, University of Arizona; Riley Drake, University of Wisconsin - Stout; Adrienne Robertson, Temple University; Carla B. Cheatham, Seattle University; Betsy Marina Perez, California State University, Northridge*

Racialized Conflict: The Role of School Counselors in Prevention and Restoration between Black Students and White Teachers. *Paul C. Harris, Virginia Commonwealth University; Audra Lancaster Boyce, Virginia Commonwealth University; Jessica Fort, Virginia Commonwealth University*

Amplifying Student Perspectives: Exploring the Role of Student Voice in School Counseling Practices. *Chelsea Hilliard, Fairfield University; Jordon Beasley, Augusta University; Ian Levy, Rutgers University; Kara Ieva, Rowan University; Natalie Edirmanasinghe, California State University - Long Beach*

Through Their Eyes: Black Girls Reimagining the Future of School Mental Health Post-COVID-19 through Youth Participatory Action Research. *Christina Tillery, Virginia Commonwealth University*

Co-Constructing Healing-Centered Educator SEL: A Critical Participatory Action Research Study of School Counselor Praxis. *Kara Ieva, Rowan University; Erica Figueroa, Rowan University; Melissa Franzosi, Rowan University; Indra L. Owens, Rowan University; Jordon Beasley, Augusta University; Sam Steen, George Mason University*

Chair: *Ian Levy, Rutgers University*

Discussant: *Erik Hines, George Mason University*

25.026. New Directions in Black Educational History. Division F - Historical Inquiry in Education; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 504;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

New Geographies of Black Education: Literacy in the 1823 Demerara Rebellion. *Darien Dey, Harvard University*

Black School Spirit and Critical Archival Recovery at Kentucky's First Black Public High School. *Jordan Jackson-Collins, Harvard University*

A Critical History of Black Higher Education: Institutional Death and the Black College. *Cassandra Hanna, Harvard University*

The Black Teacher in 19th Century Britain and its Empire. *Esther Anfo-Whyte, Harvard University*

Chair: *kihana miraya ross, Northwestern University*

Discussant: *Zenzile Saharee Riddick, Northwestern University*

25.027. Beyond Mentoring: Muxerista, Feminista, and Black Feminist Approaches to Femtorship. Division G - Social Context of Education; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304C;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Theorizes Muxerista Femtorship through collective writing, pláticas, and convivencia to resist spirit murder in academia. *Anita Tijerina Revilla, California State University - Los Angeles; Dolores Delgado Bernal, Loyola Marymount University; Diana Ponce, University of California - San Francisco; Katherine E Coronado, California State University - Los Angeles; Cythia Alonso, California State University - Los Angeles*

Muxerista Factorship: Recuerdos, Resistencia, y Reimagining Peer Muxerista Mentoring. *Lucila D. Ek, University of Texas - San Antonio; Iliana Alanis, University of Texas - San Antonio; Patricia D. Quijada Cerecer, University of California - Davis*

Chicana/x Feminista Femtorship: From Ph.D. to Profesora. *Nancy Huante-Tzintzun, California State University - Sacramento; Socorro Morales, California State Polytechnic University - Pomona; Sylvia Mendoza, University of Texas - San Antonio*

From the Farm to the Ph.D.: Grandmother's Mother Wit as Epistemology & Pedagogies of Dirt. *Amina Humphrey, El Camino College*

Chair: *Dolores Delgado Bernal, Loyola Marymount University*

Discussant: *Anita Tijerina Revilla, California State University - Los Angeles*

25.028. Learning Across Contexts. Division G - Social Context of Education; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 303A;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Beyond Language Mastery: Belonging and Educational Equity for Multilingual Youth in Hong Kong. *Huseyin Uysal, The Education University of Hong Kong*

Disengaged or Disillusioned? A Generational Analysis of Online Talk on Learning Motivation. *Hyojung Kim, Indiana University*

Teachers' Discursive Constructions of 'Learning' in Neoliberal Times: Insights from a Chinese Public Middle School. *Yunshu Zhu, Qufu Normal University*

Academic Success of Youth in the Juvenile Legal System: Examining the Impact of School Transitions. *Tia Ross, Retired; Nisha Manikoth, Hood College*

Landscape Scan of Media Literacy Education: A Situated Educational Inquiry for State Policymakers and School Leaders. *Renee Hobbs, University of Rhode Island; Yonty Friesem, Columbia College Chicago; Catherine Morris, Media Education Lab, Inc.*

Chair: *Sarah Priscilla Lee, Northwestern University*
Discussant: *Nisha Acharya Julien, Opportunity Consulting*

25.029. Youth Participatory Action Research with Asian American Communities: Methodological Innovations and Transformative Possibilities. Division G - Social Context of Education; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 301A;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Unsettling Possibilities: Navigating the Methodological, Political, and Ethical Tensions of Youth Participatory Action Research with Asian American and Migrant Youth. *Yeji Kim, University of Missouri*

Paths and Impediments: Reflections on Conducting YPAR alongside Asian American Youth in the U.S. Northeast. *Ankhi Guha Thakurta, Boston College; Yueyang Shen, Boston College; Deepshikha Banerjee, Boston College*

“History in school never taught me about where I fit”: Asian American Youth Disrupting Curriculum Violence Through Youth Participatory Action Research. *Roland Sintos Coloma, Wayne State University; Jungmin Kwon, Michigan State University; Wenyang Sun, University of Utah; Min Yu, Wayne State University; Pyeongeun Kim, Michigan State University; Seungwoo Hwang, Michigan State University*

“Our Folks Were Badass!”: Learning, Dreaming, and Organizing in a Youth-Led Asian American History Collective. *Sohyun An, Kennesaw State University*

Chairs: *Wenyang Sun, University of Utah; Jungmin Kwon, Michigan State University; Min Yu, Wayne State University; Roland Sintos Coloma, Wayne State University*

Discussant: *Allyson Tintiango-Cubales, San Francisco State University*

25.030. Are There Stages to This? The Case For (and Against) Research-Practice Partnership Developmental Trajectories. Division H - Research, Evaluation and Assessment in Schools; Structured Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 515A;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

1. Emergent Evaluation in Pioneering Research-Practice Partnerships: Insights from the First RPP in France (Poster 1). *Denis Pasco, University of Franche-Comté*
2. Using Partnership Accountability to Promote Organizational Learning: A Case Study Exploring RPP Growth (Poster 2). *Diana G. Mercado-Garcia, California Education Partners*
3. The Ebb and Flow of Using Survey Measures As Research-Practice Partnerships Evolve (Poster 3). *Laura P. Wentworth, California Education Partners*
4. Developing Identities as Researchers in Research-Practice Partnerships: A Case Study of an Innovative Postdoctoral Program (Poster 4). *Elizabeth Zumpe, University of Oklahoma; Rachel Ruggirello, Washington University in St.*

Louis; Andrew C. Butler, Washington University in St. Louis; Katherine Ashton, University of Oklahoma

5. Identifying Phases of Partnership Work: Commonalities and Differences Across Eight Computer Science Research-Practice Partnerships (Poster 5). *Daniel Schmidt, Partner to Improve; Erin C. Henrick, Vanderbilt University*
6. The Case With the Theory-Practice Divide: Evaluation of Research-Practice Partnerships From a German Perspective (Poster 6). *Sandra Fischer-Schöneborn, IU International University of Applied Sciences; Timo Ehmke, Leuphana University - Lueneburg*
7. Testing Hypothetical Developmental Trajectories for Research-Practice Partnerships (Poster 7). *Alison Fox Resnick, University of Colorado - Boulder; Corinne Singleton, Menlo Education Research; Caitlin Farrell, University of Colorado - Boulder; Kristina M. Stamatis, University of Nebraska Omaha; William R. Penuel, University of Colorado - Boulder*
8. Phases, Stages, or Something Else? What Other Non-RPP Evaluation Frameworks Reveal About RPP Evolution (Poster 8). *Simon Sjölund, Mälardalen University; Paula Arce-Trigatti, National Network of Education Research-Practice Partnerships*

Chair: *Paula Arce-Trigatti, National Network of Education Research-Practice Partnerships*

Discussant: *Caitlin Farrell, University of Colorado - Boulder*

25.031. Collaboration, Teamwork, and Interprofessional Learning. Division I - Education in the Professions; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum B; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

- A Model of Teamwork in Graduate Medical Education: One Step in Developing a Formative Assessment. *Monica M. Cuddy, NBME; Marcia L. Winward, National Board of Medical Examiners; Ujjayini Das, University of Maryland*
- From ‘Who I Am’ to ‘What I Be’: Pathways to Emotional Intelligence in Interprofessional Learning. *Helen Qing He, University of Hong Kong; Jiahao Liang, University of Hong Kong; Fraide A. Ganotice, University of Hong Kong*
- How does social support influence interprofessional team efficacy and goal attainment among health professional students? A mediation analysis. *Fraide A. Ganotice, University of Hong Kong; Xiaoi Shen, University of Hong Kong; John Ian Wilzon Tolentino Dizon, University of Hong Kong; Helen Qing He, University of Hong Kong*
- “Let’s Practice Together”: Exploring Collaborative Virtual Reality for Nursing Students’ IVPB Medication Administration Training. *Yupei Duan, University of Missouri; Xinhao Xu, University of Missouri; Jhon Buenovesga, Pennsylvania State University; Shangman Li, University of Missouri; Michelle Cox, Pennsylvania State University; Yuanyuan Gu, University of Missouri; Sue Yun*

Fowler, University of Missouri; Hillary L. Claunch, University of Missouri

Chair: *Curtis G. Jefferson, University of Washington*

Discussant: *Ellen L. Usher, Mayo Clinic*

25.032. Statewide Developmental Education Reform in California: Lessons From A Five-Year Mixed-Methods Study. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Symposium JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum I; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Developmental Education Reform and Student Outcomes at California Community Colleges. *Lauren Schudde, University of Texas at Austin; Wonsun Ryu, University of Texas at Austin; Dae Y. Kim, Research for Action; Taylor Stanley, Research for Action*

Comparing California Community College Faculty Perceptions of Student Success with Trends in Administrative Data. *Kri Burkander, Research for Action; Taylor Stanley, Research for Action*

Comparing Costs and Impacts of Various Cocurricular Support Models. *Xinhe Liu, Teachers College, Columbia University; Dae Y. Kim, Research for Action*

Everybody Else is Doing it, So Why Can't We? Challenges and Variations of Corequisite Remediation. *Mark Duffy, Research for Action; Kri Burkander, Research for Action; Molly Pileggi, Research for Action*

Chair: *Taylor Stanley, Research for Action*

Discussants: *Federick Ngo, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Valerie Lundy-Wagner, California Community Colleges*

25.033. Technology and Student Learning. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Paper Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum G; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Computing Identity Development for Mixed Experience Students in Hispanic Serving Community College Artificial Intelligence Courses. *Paul Charles Bigby, Virginia Tech; Sarah Rodriguez, Virginia Tech; Antanjot Kaur, Virginia Tech; Kylee Shiekh, Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University; Benjamin Chaback, Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University*

Consequences of Mental Fatigue in Online Higher Education: A Scoping Review. *Fatemeh Marzban, Texas Tech University; Fethi A. Inan, Texas Tech University; Deniz Unal, Texas Tech University*

Mapping Gender Disparities and Academic Persistence in STEM Higher Education: A Systematic and Bibliometric Review. *Francisca Beroiza-Valenzuela, Universidad de las Américas (UDLA), Chile; Daniela Véliz Calderón, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile*

Beyond Barriers: How Risk Perceptions Moderate Students' Generative AI Adoption in Higher Education. *Jie Lin,*

Shanghai Jiao Tong University

Navigating AI in Higher Education: Student Views on Professors' Attitude of AI Tools in the Classroom Analyzed through Sentiment Analysis and Topic Modeling. *Xingchen Wei, Vanderbilt University; Jialing Wu, The Ohio State University*

Discussant: *Krisanna L. Machtmes, Ohio University*

25.034. The PASS Project: Reflections on a Decade of Research (Division J, Vice Presidential Session). Division J - Postsecondary Education; Symposium JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum H; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Ten Years of PASS Project: Reflections on a Longitudinal Research-to-Practice Study (Division J Vice Presidential Session). *Adrianna Kezar, University of Southern California*
Nurturing a Decade-Long Research-Practice Partnership: Initiating and Sustaining Relationships. *Rosemary J. Perez, University of Michigan; Liane I. Hypolite, California State Polytechnic University - Pomona*

Mixing Methods for Practical, Scholarly, and Theoretical Impact. *Joseph Kitchen, University of Southern California; Ralitsa Todorova, University of Southern California*
Ecological Validation: A Key [Redacted] Study Theoretical Contribution. *Ronald Hallett, University of Southern California*

The Practical Implications of [redacted] Project: Key Practitioner-Oriented Findings and Open-Access Deliverables. *Zoë Corwin, University of Southern California; Amy Goodburn, University of Nebraska - Lincoln*

Chair: *Ralitsa Todorova, University of Southern California*

Discussant: *Adrianna Kezar, University of Southern California*

25.035. Transnational Student Experiences within Higher Education: Developments and Possibilities. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Paper Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum F; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Amid Global-National-Local Dynamics: Students' Rational Choices and Transitions in Transnational Higher Education in China. *Yang Hang, Soochow University; Rong Wang, Xi'an Jiaotong-Liverpool University*

Future Student Learning and Transformation Through Collaborative Problem-Based Projects in Rural Slovenian Communities. *Klavdija Zorec, Faculty of Information Studies, Slovenia*

The Golden Mean: How Zhongyong Thinking Affects College Students' Career Adaptability and the Pathways. *Xiaoyu Wang, Beijing Normal University; Yufeng Zhang, Beijing Normal University*

Transformative Learning through Racial Encounters: International Students' Critical Reflections in U.S. Higher

Education. *Sarang Kim, University of Oklahoma*

Chair: *Blanca Solis, University of South Florida*

Discussant: *Haishan Yang, University of Southern California*

25.036. Humanizing Professional Learning: Equity, Agency, and Well-being Across California Subject Matter Projects. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 8; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Integrating Computational Thinking in STEM: Supporting Teacher Efficacy Through Professional Learning. *Maria Chiara Simani, University of California - Riverside; Jon Kovach, University of California - Irvine*

Focal Students as Catalysts for Equity in Mathematics Lesson Study. *Kyndall A. Brown, University of California - Los Angeles*

Transforming World Language Pedagogy Statewide Through Standards-Based Professional Learning. *Margaret Peterson, Stanford University; Eduardo Rafael Munoz-Munoz, San José State University*

Chair: *Claudia Louise Martinez, University of California, Office of the President*

Discussant: *Alejandro Sandoval, University of California*

25.037. Mentoring from the Margins: Preparing and Sustaining Teachers of Color for Educational Equity. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 9; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

A Scoping Review of the Research Literature on Black Male Educator Retention. *Jahmere G Jackson, Howard University; Nathan Alexander, Howard University*

Beyond Compliance: Reimagining Mentoring for Teachers of Color. *Francesca R. Ho Sang, Hunter College*

BIPOC Teacher Development as a Catalyst for Shaping Future Norms in Recruitment and Retention Practices. *Alex Guzman, Kean University; David Antunes, Rutgers University; Madji Fall, Kean University; Eleni Zgourou, Kean University*

Reimagining Mentoring: Pláticas-Testimonios of Latinx Teachers in Southern California. *Natalie Marie Carter, Claremont Graduate University*

The Right to Belong: Minority Male Teachers' Reflections in a Post-Secondary Teacher Preparation Mentoring Program. *Gilberto P. Lara, University of Texas - San Antonio; Langston Clark, University of Texas at San Antonio; Xavier Lored, University of Texas - San Antonio; Victor Hugo Martin, University of Texas - San Antonio*

Discussant: *Saili S. Kulkarni, San Jose State University*

25.038. Navigating Borderlands: Stories of Teachers Shaping Justice-Oriented Classrooms. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 7; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

A Queer Lenticular Analysis of Learning to Teach: Bilingual Special Educators in Alternative, Synchronous-Service Preparation. *Devon Hedrick-Shaw, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Pláticas with First Generation Latina Teachers (FGLTs): Navigation of Nепantla in Oregon's Educational Borderlands. *Rebecca Renea Ramirez Larson, Lewis & Clark College*

Preservice teachers' perception of the impact of social movement on their career aspirations. *Huixuan Xu, The Education University of Hong Kong*

Teaching Ethnic Studies during a Complex Time: K – 12 Ethnic Studies Educators in California. *Angeles Rubi Castorena, University of California - Irvine*

Chair: *Devon Hedrick-Shaw, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Discussant: *Jeffery Franklin, Indiana University - Indianapolis*

25.039. Reading and Writing about Climate Change: Developing Teachers' Literacies in/for a Warming World. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 6; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Engaging Teachers in Professional Development For Teaching About Climate Change. *Fawn E. Canady, Southern Oregon University; Richard W. Beach, University of Minnesota; Troy W. Hicks, Central Michigan University*

The Power of a Transnational Exchange of Bilingual Poems to Build Climate Literacies with Educators. *Lina Trigos-Carrillo, Universidad del Norte; Nicole R. Misra, University of Missouri - St. Louis; Luzkarime Calle-Diaz, Institución Educativa El Recuerdo; Rebecca L. Rogers, University of Missouri - St. Louis*

Slowing our Laments: Encouraging Teacher Socioecological Literacies amidst Climate Crisis. *Alexandra Panos, University of South Florida; Kristin Valle Geren, University of South Florida; Jarod Roselló, University of South Florida; Mieke Valk, Polk County Schools*

Supporting Teachers' Speculative Civic Literacies through Hopeful Climate Fiction (Cli Fi) Writing. *Rebecca Woodard, University of Illinois at Chicago; Andrea Vaughan, University of Illinois at Chicago; Kate Sjostrom, University of Illinois at Chicago; Kristine Wilber, University of Illinois at Chicago*

Walking and Writing as Ethical and Emergent Literacy Practices of Engagement in English Language Arts. *Michelle*

A. Honeyford, University of Manitoba; Jennifer Watt, University of Manitoba

Discussant: *Alexandra Panos, University of South Florida*

25.040. Teacher Isolation in the Post-Digital Era: Challenges and Opportunities for Developing Teacher Networks Today. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Working Group Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 501A;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

How Elon Musk contributed to the demise of the #OakEd network. *Jeffrey P. Carpenter, Elon University*

Into the Shadows, Out of the Streets: Teacher Activist Networks and the Public Square in the Post-Digital, Post-COVID Era. *Kira J. Baker-Doyle, University of Illinois at Chicago*

Technology-Mediated Professional Learning is Associated with Evolving Rural Science Teacher Networks. *Rebecca Sansom, Texas A&M University; Syahrul Amin, Texas A&M University*

TEFL in Rural Schools of Uruguay: Designing a Network of Practice to Enhance Language Teaching. *Valentina Alpuin, University of Illinois at Chicago; Vanessa Z Mari, Nevada State College*

Design Tensions and Opportunities for Building a Sustainable Professional Learning Network. *Chulin Chen, University of Tennessee; Joshua Rosenberg, University of Tennessee; Amy Maples, University of Tennessee; Lynn L. Hodge, University of Tennessee*

Chair: *Bret Staudt Willet, Florida State University*

25.041. Unforgetting, Designing, Reimagining: Equitable Futures in Math Ed Tech for Teachers and Learners. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 1;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Unforgetting the Roots: Defining Essential Characteristics of Culturally Responsive Math Education for Ed Tech Design. *Saroja Warner, Wested; Rebecca Colina Neri, Stemuli Studios, Inc.; Aleata Hubbard Cheoua, WestEd*

Designing for Emotional and Relational Dimensions: Guidelines for Advancing SEL in Math Ed Tech. *Rista Plate, Collaborative for Academic, Social, and Emotional Learning; Heather Schwartz, CASEL*

From Framework to Feature: Examples of Culturally Responsive and SEL-Aligned Math Ed Tech in Action. *Julie Jackson Cohen, University of Virginia; Taylor Shead, Stemuli Studios; Rachel Etienne, Reconstruction*

Embedded Learning: A Model for Supporting Teacher Development Through Justice-Aligned EdTech. *Rebecca Colina Neri, Stemuli Studios, Inc.; Saroja Warner, Wested; Aleata Hubbard Cheoua, WestEd*

Chair: *Titiola Harley, Bill Gates Foundation*

Discussant: *Korah Wiley, Digital Promise*

25.042. Policy Without Borders: Rethinking Higher Education Reform Across Nations and Narratives. Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 2;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Governing the Displacement: A Critical Policy Study of UNHCR's Education Strategies. *Annan Turan, Arizona State University*

Making Equitable Change: A Meta-Synthesis of Instructional Change Efforts for Marginalized Student Groups. *Rachel L. Renbarger, FHI 360; Ying Wang, FHI 360; Taylor Boyd, Western Michigan University; Emily Bolger, Michigan State University; Noah Finkelstein, University of Colorado - Boulder; Charles R. Henderson, Western Michigan University; M. Danny Caballero, Michigan State University; Andrea L. Beach, Western Michigan University; Scott P. Simkins, North Carolina A&T State University*

Reforming Higher Education in Kazakhstan: Conflict between Global Aspirations and Local Realities. *Dilrabo Jonbekova, Nazarbayev University; Aida Sagintayeva, Nazarbayev University; Sulushash Kerimkulova, Nazarbayev University*

The Chilling Effects of Anti-DEI Legislation on College/University Faculty, Staff, and Graduate Students. *Brianne Kramer, Southern Utah University*

Understanding Public Perspectives: A Comment-Based Analysis of U.S. Higher Education Policy Reform. *Cecilia Bibbo, University at Albany - SUNY*

Chair: *Emily E. Virtue, Western Carolina University*

Discussant: *Edwin Nii Bonney, Clemson University*

25.043. The Politics of Autonomy: Academic Freedom and Governance in Global Higher Education. Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 10; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

The Politics of Institutional Neutrality in Higher Education: Ambiguity, Fear, and Democratic Erosion. *Curtis Anthony Brewer, University of Texas - San Antonio; Michelle D. Young, University of California - Berkeley*

Populist Power against Academic Autonomy: The Right-Wing Assault on Israeli Universities. *Halleli Pinson, Ben Gurion University of the Negev*

Academic Freedom in Practice: A Conceptual Framework and Workshop Design for Faculty Legal Empowerment. *Shaimaa Ibrahim, William & Mary*

Protected but Precarious: First Amendment Rights for International Students. *Junyan (Emma) Zhu, Baylor University*

Discussant: *William C. Purdy, University of California - Los*

SIG Sessions

25.044. Profiles, Perspectives, and Pressures: Understanding Adolescent Flourishing, Motivation, and Relationships in Singapore. SIG-Adolescence and Youth Development;

Symposium

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 303B;

1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Understanding Student Flourishing Through Latent Profiles of Adolescents in Singapore. *Kenneth Poon, Nanyang Technological University - National Institute of Education; Melvin Chan, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University; Trivina Kang, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University; Ser Hong Tan, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University; Gregory Arief D. Liem, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University; Imelda Santos Caleon, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University; Rebecca P. Ang, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University; Kiat Hui Khng, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University; Azi Jamaludin, Nanyang Technological University; Siow Chin Ng, Ministry of Education - Singapore; Chiew Lim Lee, Nanyang Technological University - National Institute of Education*

Career Clarity and Uncertainty among Early Adolescents in Singapore: Does it matter, how and for whom? *Melvin Chan, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University; Gregory Arief D. Liem, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University; Trivina Kang, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University*

Peering into the "Black Box" of Parental and Peer Relationships. *Trivina Kang, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University; Nur Qamarina Binte Ilham, Nanyang Technological University - National Institute of Education; Janelle Shaina Ng, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University; Imelda Santos Caleon, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University*

How do Achievement Goals Affect Students' Adjustment in Secondary School? *Ser Hong Tan, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University; Gregory Arief D. Liem, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University; Rebecca P. Ang, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University; Liyana Safii, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University; Jin Nen Wong, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University; Aerial Lin, National Institute of Education - Nanyang*

Technological University; Jia Min Low, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University

Hidden Pathways of Potential: Profiling Psychosocial Diversity in Financially Disadvantaged Singapore Adolescents. *Azi Jamaludin, Nanyang Technological University; Chiang Wee Heng, Ministry of Education - Singapore; Sandeep Singh, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University; Aik Lim Tan, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University; Ser Hong Tan, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University; Imelda Santos Caleon, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University; Andy Khong, Nanyang Technological University*

Chair: *Kenneth Poon, Nanyang Technological University - National Institute of Education*

Discussant: *Liesel Ebersohn, University of Pretoria*

25.045. NPD Grant-Project Based Research: Constructing a New Vision for Effective MLL Teacher Education. SIG-Bilingual Education Research; Symposium

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 506;

1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

The SEL-e-SIOP Model: An Innovative and Effective Approach for MLL Teacher Education. *Rui Niu-Cooper, Grand Valley State University; Jeffrey D. Greene, Western Michigan University*

Reaching All Individuals and Communities to Establish Success in Language Learning. *Chrissy J Cross, Stephen F. Austin State University; Heather K. Olson Beal, Stephen F. Austin State University; Marisol Diaz, California State Polytechnic University - Pomona*

Empowering Rural Educators of Multilingual Learners: Insights from a Five-Year Professional Learning Project. *Anshika Bhasin, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Jennifer Wilfrid, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Elizabeth M. Cranley, WIDA; Rebecca E. Sawyer, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Chair: *Rui Niu-Cooper, Grand Valley State University*

Discussant: *Marisol Diaz, California State Polytechnic University - Pomona*

25.046. Mentoring Emerging Researchers on Developing Conceptual Framework for Scholarly Inquiry. SIG-

Constructivist Theory, Research, and Practice; Demonstration/Performance

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, San Gabriel A; 1:45-3:15pm

Participant:

Mentoring Emerging Researchers on Developing Conceptual Framework for Scholarly Inquiry. *Justina Ogodo, Baylor University*

Chair: *Justina Ogodo, Baylor University*

Participants: *Dana Morris, University of Texas - Tyler; Marsha E.*

Simon, Valdosta State University; Maggie Bryant, Baylor University; Joshua Jonas, Baylor University; Toyosi Stephen Adedara, Baylor University; Krystle Moos, Baylor University; Kristen Davis, Baylor University

25.047. Shaking the Table: Centering the Voices of Identity Center Practitioners. SIG-Critical Educators for Social Justice; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304A;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Telling My Truth: A Black Woman Scholar's Journey Through Self-Inquiry and Storytelling in the Academy. *Dana Murray Patterson, Wingate University*

My Ethnic Studies Kuwento: Healing and Liberation through Student Resource Centers. *Michael R. Manalo-Pedro, Pomona College*

Partners in Justice: The Origin Story of a MENA Cultural Center. *Marcela Ramirez-Stapleton, University of California*

(Re)Imagining the Work: Counter-Storytelling in a Time of Organizational Change. *Kandi Bauman, The Brotherhood Initiative/University of Washington*

Leading from the Middle: Reflections of a Nepantlera Navigating Identity and Supporting Students at La Casa. *Adele Lozano, University of Wisconsin - LaCrosse*

Chair: *Jonathan A. McElderry, Elon University*

Discussant: *Stephanie Hernandez Rivera, Elon University*

25.048. Wayward Fabulation and Black Feminist Imaginaries. SIG-Critical Examination of Race, Ethnicity, Class and Gender in Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 3;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

"I Thought I was Something Then!": A Transtemporal Study of Black Childhood Literacies. *CoCo Massengale, Stanford University*

I Go to Prepare a Place for You: Waymaking Literacies and Black Feminist Futures in the Academy. *Theda Gibbs Grey; Alexis Morgan Young, Michigan State University; Jennifer Danridge Turner, University of Maryland*

Cartographic Camaraderie: Extending the Black Girl Cartography Framework through Critical Cartography. *Lauren Whatley, University of Alabama*

The Quilt We Built: Designing and Facilitating Culturally Situated Inquiry for Black Undergraduates in Times of Peril. *Amber Pabon, Kutztown University of Pennsylvania*

Chair: *Cambria Conley, University of Maryland*

Discussant: *Jennifer Danridge Turner, University of Maryland*

25.049. Critical Issues in Curriculum Studies Business Meeting. SIG-Critical Issues in Curriculum and Cultural Studies; Business Meeting
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 309;

1:45-3:15pm

Chair: *Blanca Gabriela Caldas Chumbes, University of Minnesota*

25.050. Amplifying Children's Voices for Transformative Early Childhood Education. SIG-Critical Perspectives on Early Childhood Education; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304B;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Children's Perspectives on Care within U.S. Immigrant Households. *Rosangela Araujo Silva, University of Georgia; Mariana Lima Becker, University of Georgia*

Discipline and Belonging: How Early Elementary Students Make Sense of Punishment in the Classroom. *Alexandrea Henry, Stanford University*

Listening Otherwise to Immigrant Young Children: A posthumanism Reorientation. *Naewook Kwon, University of Georgia*

Remembering and Reclaiming: Reviving the Endangered Hoche Language through Children's Voices. *Jue Wang, University of Idaho*

We Want to Be Sad: Children's Calls for Honest Learning in Restrictive Times. *Kushya Sugarman, Mount Holyoke College*

Chair: *Nathaniel Bryan, University of Texas at Austin*

Discussant: *Brian L. Wright, University of Memphis*

25.051. The hidden side of emancipation: Historicizing well-intentioned educational projects. SIG-Cultural-Historical Research; Symposium
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, San Gabriel B; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Coloniality within a Revolutionary Project: Historizing the 1980 Nicaraguan Literacy Campaign. *Rafael Meza Duriez, University of California - Berkeley*

The politics of well-intentioned citizenship education in California. *Karen Eliza Villegas, University of California San Diego*

The Contradictions of Opportunity: Transfronterix Education Across Asymmetrical Border Lines. *Isaac Alejandro Felix, University of California - Berkeley*

Sustaining Anti-Black Colonial Logics Through Caring Dehumanization in a Chilean School. *Maria Eugenia Rojas Concha, Pontificia Universidad Catolica de Valparaiso*

Chair: *Cati V. de los Rios, University of California - Berkeley*

Discussant: *Alicia Rusoja, University of California - Davis*

25.052. Interrogating and Advancing Inclusive and Accessible Tech/Media Engagement for Neurodiverse Learners. SIG-Disability Studies in Education; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 511AB;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Disrupting Neuronormativity: Understanding AuDHD Experiences via TikTok. *Dana Baker, Fairleigh Dickinson University; Laura Flores Shaw, Johns Hopkins University*

Learning from Autistic Redditors: ChatGPT Adaptations and Implications for Inclusive Educational AI Design. *Yvette Doss, University of California - Santa Barbara*

Reimagining Sex Education with Autistic Youth Through a Playable Online Game. *Jenny Sperling, University of Oklahoma; Jaye Capretto, University of Oklahoma Health Sciences Center; Gale Hann, University of Oklahoma*

The Boundaries and Possibilities of Inclusion: Chinese Audience Responses to On-Screen Representations of Autism. *Jianglan Ding, South China Normal University; Xiaomeng Chen, South China Normal University*

Discussant: *Alan R. Foley, Syracuse University*

25.053. Scaling Out, Up, and Deep: Mobile Making Afterschool Program across Four California State University Campuses. SIG-Informal Learning Environment Research; Structured Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 515B;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

1. The Role of Resources in Supporting STEM Interest & Identity in an Afterschool Maker-based STEM Program (Poster 1). *Jasmine M. Nation, California Polytechnic State University - San Luis Obispo; Claire Gillaspie, California Polytechnic State University - San Luis Obispo; Isabella Contreras, California Polytechnic State University - San Luis Obispo; Ellie Jordyn Farrar, California State Polytechnic University - San Luis Obispo; Ava Ghaffari-Kashani, California State Polytechnic University - San Luis Obispo; Jessica Jensen, California Polytechnic State University - San Luis Obispo; Kristin Bridgeford, California State Polytechnic University - Pomona*
2. Investigating Youth Perceptions, Interest, and Confidence: Affordances and Limitations of Maker-based STEM activities in Upper Elementary School (Poster 2). *Samantha Caldera, California State University - Fresno; Alexandria K. Hansen, California State University - Fresno; Cristian De La Torre, California State University - Fresno; Amaya De Vore, California State University - Fresno; Myunghwan Shin, California State University - Fresno*
3. STEM Tinkering in the Library: Finding Evidence for Science Learning (Poster 3). *James F. Kisiel, California State University - Long Beach; Nicholas Franco, California State University - Long Beach*
4. Near-peer Mentors Draw On and Build Cultural Capital as Mobile Making Facilitators (Poster 4). *Kayleen Diaz, California State University - San Marcos; Edward Price, California State University - San Marcos; Brean Prefontaine, Duke University; Raquel Yoshinaga, California State University - San Marcos; Mallory Rice, California State University - San Marcos*

5. Investigating the Impact of Facilitating Maker-based STEM Activities on College Students' Interest and Confidence in STEM (Poster 5). *Amaya De Vore, California State University - Fresno; Alexandria K. Hansen, California State University - Fresno; Samantha Caldera, California State University - Fresno; Myunghwan Shin, California State University - Fresno*
 6. From Making to Becoming: Preservice Teachers' Pathways in STEM through Service Learning (Poster 6). *Myunghwan Shin, California State University - Fresno; Alexandria K. Hansen, California State University - Fresno; Sinem Siyahhan, California State University - San Marcos*
 7. Building and Cultivating Community Partnerships across Contexts: Lessons Learned from the Mobile Making Program (Poster 7). *April Nelson, California State University - San Marcos; James F. Kisiel, California State University - Long Beach; Katherine Huotari, California State University - Long Beach*
 8. Why Do They Come? Understanding Youth Participation in a Library-based Maker Program (Poster 8). *Zulema Morales, Aquarium of the Pacific; James F. Kisiel, California State University - Long Beach*
 9. Evaluation of the Mobile Making Program: Scalability and Sustainability (Poster 9). *James Marshall, San Diego State University; Sinem Siyahhan, California State University - San Marcos; Edward Price, California State University - San Marcos*
- Chair: *Sinem Siyahhan, California State University - San Marcos*
Discussant: *Kylie A. Pepler, University of California - Irvine*

25.054. Incorporating Transformative Frameworks into Mixed Methods Research: Challenges, Insights, and Recommendations. SIG-Mixed Methods Research; Symposium
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, K-Town; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

- Advancing Equity for Disabled College Students: An Application of Guiding Questions for Transformative Mixed Methods. *Elisabeth Kutscher, The George Washington University; Valerie L. Mazzotti, University of Kansas*
- Critical Race Mixed Methodology (CRMM) As A Transformative Method: The Benefits and Challenges. *Jessica T. Decuir-Gunby, University of Southern California*
- Reframing Sampling as a Transformative Act in Explanatory Sequential Mixed Methods Research. *Tashane Haynes-Brown, University of the West Indies, Mona*
- Chairs: *Analay Perez, University of Michigan; Matthew T. McCrudden, Pennsylvania State University; Sergi Fàbregues2, Universitat Oberta de Catalunya*
- Discussant: *Peggy Shannon-Baker, Georgia Southern University*

25.055. Forging New Harmonies: Lived Experience and Student-Centered Praxis in Music Education. SIG-Music

Education; Symposium

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Georgia I;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Black identities and Experiences in Music Education Spaces:
Constructing a New Vision by Disrupting Anti-Blackness.

Colin Walters, University of Connecticut; Drew Xavier Coles, Teachers College, Columbia University

Creating Equitable and Affirming Environments for Black
Individuals in Our Music Education Communities.

Drew Xavier Coles, Teachers College, Columbia University; Marjoris V. Regus, Rutgers University; Adrian Davis, University of Minnesota; Colin Walters, University of Connecticut; Darrin Thornton, Pennsylvania State University

Music Education as Intentional Community Building.

Drew Xavier Coles, Teachers College, Columbia University;

Tatyana Louis-Jacques, University of North Texas

Chair: *Drew Xavier Coles, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Discussant: *Joyce M. McCall, Arizona State University*

25.056. Inquiries of Liberation: Creativity, Solidarity, and Resistance in Qualitative Research.

SIG-Qualitative

Research; Paper Session

InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Echo

Park; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Running towards freedom in educational research: Fugitive
methodology as liberation. *Andrea Dziengue, Georgia State University; Jennifer R. Esposito, Georgia State University*

Relational Emergence as Affective Solidarity in Feminist

Qualitative Research: Beyond the “Performative DEI
Aesthetic”. *Alycia M. Elfreich, Montana State University*

Methodological Refusal: How Songwriting as Composite

Counterstorytelling is an Act of Resistance. *April M. Jones, University of Montevallo*

BUSOG Methodology: Becoming Full and Whole as Fuel for

the Resistance. *Valerie Fernandez, San Francisco State University*

Radical Interdisciplinarity: Qualitative Refusal under

Algorithmic Entropy. *Lorien S. Jordan, University of South Florida; Shavawn Smith, Arkansas Archeological Survey;*

Rachel Piontak, University of Arkansas at Fayetteville

Chair: *Jori N. Hall, University of Illinois at Chicago*

Discussant: *Giovanni P. Dazzo, University of Georgia*

25.057. Culturally Sustaining Pedagogies in Mathematics Education: Constructing a New Vision for Research and Classroom Practices.

SIG-Research in Mathematics

Education; Symposium

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Georgia II;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Interrogating Anti-Ableist Potential of Cultural Historical

Activity Theory within Mathematics Education: Sustaining
Pan-Disability Culture. *Alexis Padilla, Independent Scholar; Paulo Tan, University of California - Santa Cruz*

Interrogating Inclusion: A Culturally Sustaining UDL

Framework to Address Ableism and Racism in Mathematics
Education. *Cathery Yeh, University of Texas at Austin;*

Lauren Rigby, University of Texas at Austin; Aristotle Ou, University of Texas at Austin

“I think those are mathematical”: STEM teachers’ learning

about culturally sustaining pedagogies. *Samantha Marshall, North Carolina State University; Devan MacKenzie, North Carolina State University; Hajra Fayyaz, North Carolina State University; Darryl Yong, Harvey Mudd College*

Black Joy in the High School Classroom: An Exploration into

Deeper Learning. *Toniann Maniscalco, College of William & Mary*

Mathematical Modeling for Multilingual Learners: A Gateway
for Rightful Presence. *Karen L. Terrell, Loyola University Maryland*

Equity in Action: Reimagining Teacher Preparation for
Culturally Sustaining Computational Thinking in STEM.

Wei Wei, University of California - Los Angeles; Kimberley Gomez, University of California - Los Angeles; Jesse Ha, Montclair State University; Anuradha Ghosh, Montclair State University

Chair: *Diane H. Silva Pimentel, Brown University*

Discussant: *Rochelle Gutierrez, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

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Discussant: *Rochelle Gutierrez, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

25.058. Assessment of Reading, Writing, and Language Skills Across Elementary and Middle Grades.

SIG-Research in

Reading and Literacy; Paper Session

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Beaudry A; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Comparing code-based and language-comprehension skill
profiles across early elementary grades. *Veronica Mellado De La Cruz, University of Virginia; Sarah Wellberg, University of Virginia; Carlin Conner, University of Virginia; Phoebe Leigh Kiekhofers Garfinkel, University of Virginia; Emily J. Solari, University of Virginia; James Soland, University of Virginia; Latisha Hayes, University of Virginia*

Examining Child and Word Factors for English Spelling
Development: A Longitudinal Study. *Youngsun Moon, Stanford University; Young-Suk Grace Kim, University of California - Irvine*

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Development: A Longitudinal Study. *Youngsun Moon, Stanford University; Young-Suk Grace Kim, University of California - Irvine*

College, Columbia University; Michael Hebert, University of California - Irvine

Motivation and Self-Efficacy for Reading-Related Writing Tasks: Longitudinal Factor Structure Analysis Across Compare-Contrast and Opinion Genres. *Zoi Traga-Philippakos, University of Tennessee; Jeff Labban, University of Tennessee Knoxville*

Chair: *Youngsun Moon, Stanford University*

Discussant: *Laura S. Tortorelli, Michigan State University*

25.059. Supporting Diverse Gifted Learner Needs. SIG-Research on Giftedness, Creativity and Talent; Paper Session

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Santa Barbara C; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

A Bioecological Systems View of Rural Indian High-Ability Students' College Experiences: A Longitudinal Study. *Aakash Arvind Chowkase, Yale University; Ketika Kasetwar, Shoolini University of Biotechnology and Management Sciences; Akshay Kedari, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Nachiket Panse, Independent Researcher*

Geographic and Racial Disparities in Gifted Identification in Texas Before and After COVID-19. *Vicky Weiqing Ji, University of North Texas; Candie Aguilar, University of North Texas; Travis D. Hill, University of North Texas; Jaret Hodges, University of North Texas*

Small Towns, Big Shifts: Place-Conscious Professional Learning to Identify and Serve Underrepresented Rural Gifted Students. *Norma L. Hafenstein, University of Denver*

The Impact of Income Disparity on AP Performance in Texas Schools. *Debi K. Torres, Baylor University; Jianwen Song, Baylor University; Todd Kettler, Baylor University; James Bishop, The Passionate Mind Institute*

Beyond Identification: Rethinking Giftedness Through the Lived Experiences of Black Girls. *Oriana T. Leach, Chapin Hall Center for Children at the University of Chicago*

Chair: *Jennifer H. Robins, Baylor University*

Discussant: *Andrea Frazier, Columbus State University*

25.060. Examination of Learners and Learning in PE/PETE.

SIG-Research on Learning and Instruction in Physical Education; Paper Session

Westin Bonaventure, Level 2, Echo Park; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Comparing High Intensity Interval Training and Traditional Physical Education on Cognitive Engagement of Middle Schoolers. *Bryan Thomas, Baltimore County Public Schools; Leslie K. Curda, National University*

Learning in the Deep End: Experiential Preparation of Pre-Service Teachers through Adapted Aquatics. *Michael Messerole, University of Nebraska - Omaha; Shannon C. Mulhearn, Lander University*

“Not The Right Way, That’s One Way”: High School Students’

Meanings of Physical Activity. *Yongjin Lee, University of North Carolina - Greensboro; Ben Dyson, University of North Carolina - Greensboro*

Students’ Perspectives and Experiences of Self-Compassion in a High School Physical Education Program. *Ben Dyson, University of North Carolina - Greensboro; Yongjin Lee, University of North Carolina - Greensboro; Tsz Lun Chu, University of North Carolina - Greensboro; Seunghyun Baek, SUNY - College at Cortland; Judy A. Fowler, University of North Carolina - Greensboro*

The Influence of Reciprocal, Learner-Designed, and Learner-Initiated Teaching on Student Outcomes in Sport Education. *Wei Mao, University of North Dakota; Hairui Liu, University of North Dakota; Peter A. Hastie, Auburn University*

Chairs: *Emily Jones, Illinois State University; Victoria Shiver, University of New Mexico*

Discussant: *Dominique Banville, George Mason University*

25.061. Criticality, Dialogism, and Advocacy in Online Teacher Education: Exploring Avenues and Intersections Toward Equitable Futures. SIG-Second Language Research; Symposium

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum C; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Leveraging Critical Dialogic Education to Support Preservice Teachers’ Developing Advocacy Orientations through Online Asynchronous Discussions. *Amber N. Warren, Vanderbilt University; Fares J. Karam, University of Nevada - Reno*

Dialogic Pedagogies in Digital Spaces: Online Coursework and Coaching for Advocacy in Dual-Language Bilingual Education. *Santiago Parra Giraldo, Purdue University; Ofelia Castro Schepers, Purdue University; Jennifer Renn, Purdue University*

Critical Dialogue in Roleplays with Administrators: What Teachers Learned. *Elena Andrei, Cleveland State University; April S. Salerno, University of Virginia*

Fostering Educators’ Criticality and Advocacy for Multilingual Students Through Dialogic Online Discussions. *Sora Suh, Fairleigh Dickinson University; Catherine Michener, Rowan University*

COIL as a Dialogic Third Space: Preparing Interculturally Competent and Critically Reflective Language Educators. *Yue Bian, University of Washington - Bothell; Ruiling Feng, Tianjin Normal University; Guofang Li, University of British Columbia*

Chairs: *Amber N. Warren, Vanderbilt University; Fares J. Karam, University of Nevada - Reno*

Discussant: *Amanda Kibler, Oregon State University*

25.062. Unsettling the Present: Multigenerational, Interdisciplinary Dialogues on the Past, Present, and

Futures of Inclusive Education. SIG-Special and Inclusive Education Research; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum J;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Expanding the Science of Reading: Addressing Gaps in Equity and Inclusion. *Endia J. Lindo, Texas Christian University*
Narratives of Experience from Parents of Color of Youth with Disabilities. *Tammy Ellis-Robinson, University at Albany - SUNY; Elizabeth Slusarz, University at Albany - SUNY*

Unpacking Disability Inclusion in U.S. Higher Education: Critical Discourse Analysis for Shaping the Future. *Elizabeth Harkins, William Paterson University; Audrey M. Sorrells, Texas Christian University; Rebeka Plots, Texas Christian University*

Beyond Legacy: Interrogating Special Education's Contradictions to Forge Inclusive Futures. *Allison Turner Gunter, Winston-Salem State University*

Excavating Borders, Envisioning Futures: Reimagining State Policy Guidance for Multilingual Learners with Disabilities. *Lingyu Li, Lehman College - CUNY; Yehyang Lee, Syracuse University; Inna Stepaniuk, Simon Fraser University; Dian Mawene, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Dosun Ko, Santa Clara University*

Chairs: *Audrey M. Sorrells, Texas Christian University; Dosun Ko, Santa Clara University*

Discussant: *Aydin Bal, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

25.063. Systems Thinking in K-12 Teaching. SIG-Systems

Thinking in Education; Paper Session

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, La Brea; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

A Conceptual State and Transition Model for Resilience Practice in Education. *Becky Haddad, University of Nebraska - Lincoln; Catlin M. Goodwin, Michigan State University; Aaron J. McKim, Michigan State University*

Exploring In-Service Science Teachers' Conceptions of Systems Thinking Skills and Pedagogical Strategies in Nigeria. *Monday Moju, Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University; Azka Kiran, Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University*

Supporting Socio-Ecological Systems Thinking by Engaging Secondary Teachers in Reasoning About the Food-Energy-Water Nexus. *Hannah H. Scherer, Virginia Tech; Nia McLean, Virginia Tech; Donna M. Westfall-Rudd, Virginia Tech*

Understanding CAPE as a Practical Tool for Equity in K-12 Computer Science Education. *Karanjot Kaur, University of Texas at Austin; Joshua Childs, University of Texas at Austin; Miriam Jacobson, University of Texas at Austin; Carol Fletcher, University of Texas at Austin*

Chair: *samia javed, University of Western Ontario*

Discussant: *Robert White, ECSU*

Division and SIG Roundtables

25.064. AERA Roundtable Session Wednesday 1:45 pm;
Roundtable Session

25.064-1. Centering Teachers in Systems Improvement (Table 1). Division A - Administration; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Advancing School Improvement: Evidence from a TAP System Partnership in a High-Needs District. *Handrea A. Logis, National Institute for Excellence in Teaching; Rhea Rong Ren, National Institute for Excellence in Teaching; Taneë Hudgens, National Institute for Excellence in Teaching; Joshua H. Barnett, National Institute for Excellence in Teaching*

Flourishing Teachers, Thriving Schools: Insights from Recently Retired School Division Leaders. *Karen Elaine Belter, Edmonton Public Schools*

Infrastructure for Coaches to Assist Teacher Teams to Enact Math Talk for Equitable Participation. *Bryant Jensen, Brigham Young University; Brandon G. McMillan, Brigham Young University; Shazia Akbar, Brigham Young University; Xiaohang Zhang, Brigham Young University*

Organizational Support and Teacher Professional Capital Development : The Impact of Knowledge Sharing. *Yonghong Cai, Beijing Normal University; Runjia Tang, Capital Normal University; Kai Chen, Beijing Normal University; Zhuang Yi, Chinese National Academy of Arts; Liang Chen, Beijing Normal University*

Chair: *Anysia P. Mayer, California State University, Stanislaus*

25.064-2. Global Perspectives on Educational Change: Networks, Partnerships, and Equity in Action (Table 2). Division A - Administration; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Bridging Reform and Reality: How Education Service Providers Drive School Improvement. *Rhea Rong Ren, National Institute for Excellence in Teaching; Handrea A. Logis, National Institute for Excellence in Teaching; Taneë Hudgens, National Institute for Excellence in Teaching; Joshua H. Barnett, National Institute for Excellence in Teaching*

Developing Authentic Research Practice Partnerships (RPPs) for Educational Change: perspectives on principles and practices from diverse global contexts. *Christina Murdoch Mills, University of California - Davis; Pinkie Euginia Mthembu, University of KwaZulu-Natal; Christopher James Chapman, University of Glasgow*

From Reflection to Transformation: Advancing Equity Through

Performance Assessments and Transcendent Thinking.
Seema Sidhu, Anaheim Union High School District

Knowledge Brokers in Public Education Networks: Integrating Knowledge for Professional Learning in Chile. *Mauricio Pino-Yancovic, Universidad de Chile; Gabriela Rebagliati, Universidad de Chile*

Chair: *Azmi Azam, University of Arizona*

25.064-3. Teacher Leadership, Wellbeing, and Retention (Table 3). SIG-Leadership for School Improvement; Roundtable Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Conceptualizing Aesthetic Labor as an Education Leadership Challenge: Implications for Teacher Wellbeing and Inclusive School Culture. *George Panayiotou, University of Colorado - Denver*

Reframing Teacher Leadership: A Two-Dimensional Model of Cultivation Orientations. *Fangju Jiao, Hokkaido University*
Teachers Who Stay: A Serendipitous Finding. *Sheila R. Vaidya, Drexel University*

The influence of transformational leadership on teacher well-being: The chain mediation of school cultural climate and teacher resilience. *Qi Xiu, South China Normal University; Qian Zhang, South China Normal University; Kailun Zhou, South China Normal University*

Chair: *Itauma Itauma, Northwood University*

25.064-4. Wellbeing, Equity, and Justice: Interdisciplinary Approaches to Teaching and Research in the Arts (Table 4). SIG-Arts and Inquiry in the Visual and Performing Arts in Education; Roundtable Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

A Performing Arts Curriculum Framework (PACF) for Deeper Learning High Schools of the Future. *Frances C. Furlong, College of William & Mary*

Contextualizing Inclusion: Arts, Disability, and Race Across Transnational Learning Spaces. *Min Gu, California State University - Long Beach; Zakiya Atkinson, California State University - Long Beach*

“Looking for Connection”: Arts-Based Photovoice with Youth to Explore Relationships Between Wellbeing, Nature, and Spirituality. *Laura Azzarito, Columbia University*

SO TRUTHFUL, DIRECT, REAL! Audience Response to Justice-Involved Youth. *Kelly Lynn Brady, CUNY - Graduate Center*

Chair: *William Zhou, The George Washington University*

25.064-5. Decolonizing Research Methodology In Education (Table 5). SIG-Decolonial, Postcolonial, and Anti-Colonial Studies in Education; Roundtable Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Against Extractive Research: Collective Biography as a Method of Relation and Refusal. *Dilraba Anayatova, Arizona State University; Iveta Silova, Arizona State University; Victoria Desimoni, Arizona State University*

Decolonizing Education Research and Practice: Introducing the Islamic Philosophical Perspective of Wasatiyyah. *Zahra Hazari, Florida International University; Nushrat Hoque, Florida International University; Amal Ibourk, Florida State University; Shakhnoza Kayumova, University of Massachusetts - Dartmouth*

Looking Backwards to Move Forward: Towards an African-centred Decolonial Methodological Framework of Refusal. *Kenneth Gyamerah, Ontario Tech University; Ali Ahmed, Texas Tech University*

Resisting Neoliberal Narratives: Student Activists and Palestinian Solidarity. *Sarah A. Hale, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

Trespassing with Fear: Duo Ethnographic Story Sessions at the Crossroads of Language, Religion, and Immigration in Educational Research. *Youmna Deiri, Texas A&M International University; Tanja Burkhard, Georgia State University*

Chair: *Daranee Taychachaiwongse Teng, University of Colorado - Denver*

25.064-6. Assessment and Learning Frameworks in Education for Sustainable Development (Table 6). SIG-Environmental Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

A Comprehensive Approach to Guiding Innovation in ESD Learning Assessment. *Aaron Redman, Arizona State University; Jordan King, Arizona State University - Tempe; Daniel Fischer, Leuphana University - Lueneburg*

Action-Oriented Pedagogies Toolkit for Educators: Advancing Education for Sustainable Development. *Sawaros Thanapornsanguth, Chulalongkorn University; Jonghwi Park, United Nations University*

Climate Change Activism and Radicalization Risk: An Educational Approach to Fostering Peaceful Environmental Engagement. *Claudio Melacarne, University of Siena; Claudia Banchetti, Università di Siena; Marika Rullo, university of siena; Erica Molinaro, Florida Gulf Coast University; Giovanni Telesca, Università degli Studi di Modena e Reggio Emilia*

Sustainability Learning as an Ontological Turn A Case Study of the Saemangeum Citizen Field Research Group. *HyeJung Shin, Seoul National University*

Reconstructing Sustainability Education through Faculty Transformative Learning: The Role of Centers for Teaching

Excellence. *JANETTE BRUNSTEIN, Mackenzie Presbyterian University; Mark Walvoord, University of Central Oklahoma; Alessandra Romano, University of Siena*

Chair: *Dafna Gan, The Open University of Israel*

25.064-7. Theoretical Frameworks for Hope, Crisis, and Transformation (Table 7). SIG-Environmental Education; Roundtable Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Education for Ecological Civilization. *Leonard J. Waks, Qufu Normal University, Shandong China*

School as a Landscape Structure in the Plantationocene. *Erik Elshire, University of Illinois at Chicago*

What is education on a burning planet for? An existential analysis of learning and living in a state of threat. *David E. Long, Morehead State University; Joseph Henderson, University of Vermont*

Proposal for an Ecological Pedagogy of Hope. *Kevin Patrick O'Brien, University of Denver*

Without a Possible Vaccine, Ecopedagogical Paradigm Shift Vital to Avoid Ecological Collapse. *Greg William Misiaszek, Tohoku University*

Discussant: *Tatiana Chelle Height, University of North Carolina - Charlotte*

25.064-8. Faith-Based Educational Contexts & Professional Formation (Table 8). SIG-Religion and Education; Roundtable Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Integrating and Separating: Supporting Educators' Responses to Students' Religious and Spiritual Influences on Learning.

Mona M. Abo-Zena, University of Massachusetts - Boston

Leadership Accompaniment: An Evaluative Instrument in Support of the Practice. *John Reyes, Boston College; Melodie M. Wyttenbach, Boston College; Eric Roland, Boston College*

Chair: *Gaurav Harshe, University of South Carolina*

25.064-9. Museums and Counter-Narratives: Reimagining Teacher Education and Public Pedagogy with AANHPI Communities (Table 9). SIG-Asian Americans and Pacific Islanders in Education and Research; Roundtable Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Blank Spaces and Bold Voices: Reimagining the Teaching of Asian American Experiences in Museums. *Siyao Lyu, Columbia University*

Empowering Transformative Pedagogy Through Asian Americans' Counter-Narratives for Social Justice and

Equity. *Chaehyun Lee, Southeastern Oklahoma State University*

Museum of Mothers: Critical Counter-Narratives of Two Asian American/Asian Diaspora Women Teacher Educators.

Katrina Liu, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Betina Hsieh, University of Washington

Chair: *Chaehyun Lee, Southeastern Oklahoma State University*

25.064-10. South Korean Educators: Identity, Language, and Inclusion (Table 10). SIG-Asian Americans and Pacific Islanders in Education and Research; Roundtable Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

From Esteem to Exhaustion: The Unheard Struggles of South Korean Teachers. *Paul Koh, Towson University; Sunun Park, Cheongju National University of Education; Ji Hyun Hong, Emory University*

From Name Mispronunciation to Mutual Recognition: The Collaborative Autoethnography of South Korean Non-Native English-Speaking Teachers. *Jooyoung Jeon, Teachers College, Columbia University; Elizabeth Kim, Teachers College, Columbia University; Sori Kim, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Universal Design for Learning in South Korean Deaf Education. *Jongwoo Lee, Texas Tech University*

25.065. AERA Roundtable Session Wednesday 1:45 pm - Gold 1; Roundtable Session

25.065-1. Transfer (Table 1). Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Reframing Graduating "On-Time": Institutional Factors Affecting in the Transfer Journey. *Caitlin P. Ng, University of California - Santa Barbara; Tate Universe, University of California - Santa Barbara; Yasmine Dominguez-Whitehead, University of California - Santa Barbara; Malaphone Phommasa, University of California - Santa Barbara; Vanessa Woods, University of California - Santa Barbara*

Quantitative Exploratory Study on Students' Navigation Experiences with Transfer Policies in Illinois. *Jeongsan Hwang, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Karla Velasco, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Gianina R Baker, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Lorenzo D. Baber, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Fostering Transfer Student Belonging and Success in Liberal Studies. *Rosie Ojeda, California Polytechnic State University - San Luis Obispo; Dayanara Ramirez, California Polytechnic State University - San Luis Obispo; Blanca Arias, California Polytechnic State University - San Luis*

Obispo; Briana Barbosa, California Polytechnic State University - San Luis Obispo; Deisi Sinco, California Polytechnic State University - San Luis Obispo; Paola Gomez Maldonado, California Polytechnic State University - San Luis Obispo

Invisible on Campus: Experiences of Post-traditional Transfer Students in Online Engineering Bachelor's Degree Programs. *Jingjing Liu, Florida International University*
Chair: *Lindsay Byron, University of Florida*

25.065-2. Transforming inclusive environments in higher education (Table 2). Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Latent Trajectory Classes of College Students' Team Health Perceptions: Exploring Demographic and Contextual Predictors. *Qichuan Zhou, University of Michigan; Rebecca L. Matz, University of Michigan; Robin Fowler, University of Michigan*

The Role of Coping in the Relationship Between Academic Distress and PTSD Symptoms in College Students. *Danae Gaytan Sanelias, Washington University in St. Louis; Andrew C. Butler, Washington University in St. Louis; Rachel S. Martin, OneGoal*

Troubling First-Generation Status: Examining Internship Participation by Levels of Parental Education. *Hee Song, University of Wisconsin - Madison; John Zilvinskis, Binghamton University - SUNY; Kelli K Smith, Binghamton University*

Unpacking Diversity: Heterogeneous and U-Shaped Relationships between Team Diversity and Learning Outcomes. *Zhonghan Xie, University of Michigan; Rebecca L. Matz, University of Michigan; Robin Fowler, University of Michigan*

Who Feels Safe? Students' Perceptions of Campus Safety and Handgun Carry Through an Intersectional Lens. *Lee H. DeBoer, Collin College; JoHyun Kim, Texas A&M University; Katie K. Koo, University of Georgia*

25.065-3. Through Teachers' Perceptions: Recognition, Power, and Professional Realities (Table 3). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Condescending Esteem and the Contradictory Status of Teaching: How Educators Navigate Mixed Social Evaluation. *Krista Galleberg, Harvard University*

The Impact of Social Recognition Deficits on Teachers' Professional Perceptions and Practices. *Jeong-a Kim, Korean Educational Development Institute*

Teacher-Parent Power-Dynamics Overshadowing Other

Dimensions in Teacher PD Discourse about Conflicts with Parents. *Dana Vedder-Weiss, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev; Idit Fast, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev; Karin Sarfati-Shaulov, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev*

Chair: *Krista Galleberg, Harvard University*

25.065-4. Flip the Script: Reframing Teacher Education for Professional Growth, Learning, and Justice (Table 4). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Problematizing teaching competition for student teachers' professional identity formation: A Dynamic-System-Model-of-Role-Identity perspective. *Yue Peng, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Wenting Zhou, The Chinese University of Hong Kong*

Rethinking Initial Teacher Education Work Integrated Learning in Light of the Needs of Supervising Teachers. *Lucie Zundans-Fraser, Charles Sturt University; Will Letts, Charles Sturt University*

Revisiting the Two-Worlds Pitfall: Student Teachers and Scripted Curriculum. *Danielle Sutherland, Towson University; Stephanie Michelle Moody, Towson University; Bethany M. Rice, Towson University; Laura Jacobs, Towson University*

Rooted in Justice: Preparing future teachers to integrate Climate Justice Education in a community of practice. *Sumer Seiki, University of British Columbia*

Promoting Pre-Service Teachers' Professional Socialization Through Field Experiences: A Multiple-Case Study in Chinese Normal Universities. *Wenxin Gao, East China Normal University*

Chair: *Danielle Sutherland, Towson University*

25.065-5. Bridging Global and Local Education: Testing, Digital Skills, and Teacher Impact (Table 5). Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

A Critical Ethnographic Case Study on ELPAC Standardized Testing and Fifth-Grade Latinx Emergent Bilinguals: Teacher Pedagogy, Perceptions, and Attitudes that Transform Classroom Learning. *Nancy Madrid, Los Angeles Unified School District*

Beyond the Test Scores: Is Standardized Testing a Tool or a Tyrant for Global Education? *Yuan Cui, Beijing Normal University; Qian Zhao, Beijing Normal University*

English Learner Identification of Kindergarteners: Case Study of a U.S. District with High Student Enrollment. *Alicia Kim, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Pauline Ho, Reed College; Mark Chapman, University of Wisconsin -*

Madison; Haeun Kim, University of Melbourne; Jeanne Beck, ETS

Examining the Influence of Schools' Federal Designation on Teachers' Workplace Stress and Self-Efficacy. *Kimberly Michelle Seybolt, Arkansas State University; Ibrahim Duyar, Arkansas State University*

Global Patterns of Digital Competence: Comparative Insights from ICILS 2023. *Simeyye ARPACI, The George Washington University; Laura Christine Engel, The George Washington University*

Discussant: *Lina Safa, Pepperdine University*

25.065-6. Policy, Inclusion and Accessibility for Vulnerable Children (Table 6). SIG-Early Education and Child Development; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

The Protective Role of Low-Cost Child Care Policy in Families Navigating Child Temperament Challenges. *Yunqi Xie, University of Toronto - OISE; Samantha Burns, University of Guelph; Jeseca Perlman, University of Toronto - OISE; Esther Yu, University of Toronto - OISE; Michal Perlman, University of Toronto - OISE*

Two Decades of Growth in State Pre-K Investments: Is there a Tradeoff Between Access and Quality? *Casey Moran, Teachers College, Columbia University; Tyler Watts, Teachers College, Columbia University; Jade M. Jenkins, University of California - Irvine; Kenneth A. Dodge, Duke University; Mindy Lachs Rosengarten, Teachers College, Columbia University; Allison Friedman-Krauss, National Institute for Early Education Research; W. Steven Barnett, Rutgers University*

Patterns of Subsidized Child Care Stability for Children Experiencing Homelessness and Their Counterparts. *Kelvin T. Pompey, University of South Carolina; Qinyan Shen, University of South Carolina; Vasanthi Rao, University of South Carolina*

An Examination of a State Level Policy to Support Low Income Children with Disabilities and/or Special Needs to Better Access Publicly Funded Child Care (PFCC). *Katherine Kresin Delaney, University of Toledo; Laurie A. Dinnebeil, University of Toledo; William McInerney, University of Toledo*

PreK children's readiness to learn: Potential influence of state Child Care Development Fund (CCDF) policies. *Ryan Belew, University of Missouri - Kansas City*

Chair: *Katherine Kresin Delaney, University of Toledo*

25.065-7. Professional Development and Coaching (Table 7).

SIG-Early Education and Child Development; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Drawing on the self-identified needs of early childhood educators to improve early learning program supports. *Allison Boyle, Southern Education Foundation, Inc.; Max Altman, Southern Education Foundation*

Early Care and Education at its Best: Listening to the Voices of Veteran ECE Teachers. *Leah Schoenberg Muccio, University of Hawai'i at Manoa; Lea Ann Christenson, Towson University; Kevin McGowan, Bridgewater State University*

Characteristics of early childhood educators who participate in state-wide outdoor education professional development. *Ekaterina Novikova, University of Delaware; Kristin Kelly, University of Delaware; Jessica DeWese, University of Delaware; Laura Lessard, University of Delaware*

Supporting Vocabulary among Preschoolers at Risk for Developmental Language Disorder: A Teacher Professional Development Intervention. *Annemarie Hindman, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Barbara Wasik, Temple University*

From Teacher Training to Parent Engagement: Implications for Parent-Teacher Relationship and Early Childhood Outcomes. *JINGJING XU, University of Georgia; Erin E. Hamel, University of Georgia*

Chair: *Ekaterina Novikova, University of Delaware*

25.065-8. Place, Community, and Equity: Engaging Schools, Families, and Universities in Rural Learning (Table 8).

SIG-Rural Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Bridging the Divide: Community Knowledge and Rural Educators' Practices. *Stephanie Oudghiri Scherer, Purdue University*

Intergenerational Participation and Interpretation of Home Visits in Early Childhood Services. *Peijing Qiao, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Si Chen, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Xuerong Wang, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Tianyu Li, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Ming Dong Mak, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Mai Lu, China Development Research Foundation; Zhixin Du, China Development Research Foundation; Yi Qie, China Development Research Foundation*

Straight from the Workforce's Mouth: What Practitioners in Black, Rural Communities Say About Community-University Partnerships. *Kamia F Slaughter, Indiana University*

The Story of One Rural School District: A Case Study for Building Success in Iowa's Rural Schools. *Erika L. Bass, University of Northern Iowa; Vicki Oleson, University of Northern Iowa*

"Rural students can survive in the big city": Exploring rural

students' successful postsecondary transitions. *Kessa Roberts, Clemson University; Alycia Cole, Utah State University*

25.065-9. Virtual Communication in Higher Education (Table 9). Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Exploring Digital Communication Strategies for Global Talent Recruitment in Chinese Universities. *Kexin Long, Shanghai Jiao Tong University; Haroon Hakimi, Shanghai Jiao Tong University; Xiaoqiao Zhang, Shanghai Jiao Tong University*
Using LLM to Trace Public Sentiment and Policy Change Toward Canadian International Students. *Ya Xuan Wang, York University; Qiang Zha, York University*
Designing AI Education Ecosystem Indicators in Higher Education: A Delphi and AHP Approach. *Xinyi Wu, Shanghai Jiao Tong University; Qinglin Zhang, Shanghai Jiao Tong University; Feng-Kuang Chiang, Shanghai Jiao Tong University*

25.066. AERA Roundtable Session Wednesday 1:45 pm - Gold 2; Roundtable Session

25.066-1. Temporalities, Difference, and Educational Futures (Table 1). SIG-Critical Posthuman and Postfoundational Studies in Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Difference in the Differentials: A Deconstructive Reading of Differential Tuition. *Jonathan Barefield*
Pedagogies of Future Nostalgia: A Posthuman Intimate Scholarship Study of Desire, Discomfort, and Memory. *Isabella Devin Bartels, Teachers College, Columbia University*
Queer(ing) time as nonviolence (wit)hnessing. *Arisandy Johnson, Arizona State University*
Then and Now and Then: (Re/De)compos(t)ing Produces New Inquiries. *Rebecca C. Christ, Florida International University; Candace R. Kuby, University of Missouri*
What do Assemblage Studies do? Looking for the Politics in the Assemblage of Assemblage Studies. *Jerry L. Rosiek, University of Oregon; Sage Hatch, University of Oregon*
Chair: *Amalie Strange, Arizona State University*

25.066-2. Women and the Superintendency (Table 2). SIG-Research on Women and Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Are Women Advancing in Educational Leadership? A Study of Representation in Administration in Alberta. *Kimberly St Andre, University of Portland*

Holding the Line and Each Other: Disrupting Isolation in the Superintendency for Women. *Katrina Struloeff, University of Pennsylvania; Shanae Neal, Southern Methodist University; Megan MacDonald, University of Pennsylvania*

The Hesitation Cycle: How Social Conditioning Shapes Women's Leadership Journeys to the Superintendency. *Sally Jarvis-Lubbe, California State University - Fullerton; Daniel Sung-Yeol Choi, California State University - Fullerton; Allan John Mucerino, California State University - Fullerton*

Institutional Mediation of Educational Discourse: A Comparative Study of Technocratic and Gendered Metaphors in China, Flemish, and International Organizations. *Xinyi Li, Vrije Universiteit Brussel*

25.066-3. Everyday Resilience: Research on Families, Youth, and Adaptation (Table 3). SIG-Stress, Coping, and Resilience; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Bridging the Gap: A Scoping Review of Interventions Targeting Caregiver Mental Health in Sub-Saharan Africa. *Stansilaus James Marobo, Oakland University; Hunter C King, Oakland University; Ethan Mair, Oakland University; Kwame S Sakyi, Oakland University; Tomoko Wakabayashi, Oakland University*

Early Childhood Adversity and Science Learning: Exploring the Mediating Role of Executive Functioning. *Paola del Campo, Pennsylvania State University; Carlomagno Panlilio, Pennsylvania State University*

Exploring the Relationships among Cultural Values, Psychological Resilience, and Depression: A Study of Taiwanese Adolescents. *Ming-Hui Li, St. John's University; Chi-Chau Lin, Tunghai University; Ping-Hsien Lin, Tunghai University*

Impact of Raising a Child with MEDB Conditions: Family Resilience. *Yuyan Xia, University of Kentucky; Yaoying Xu, Virginia Commonwealth University; Chin-Chih Chen, Virginia Commonwealth University; Fa Zhang, Open University of China; Jamie L. Cage, Virginia Commonwealth University*

Mediating Roles of Self-Control and Mobile Phone Dependence in the Relationship between Anxiety and Bedtime Procrastination. *Xingyan Zhang, East China Normal University; Yi Jiang, East China Normal University*
Chair: *Cynthia Arraya Wiltshire, University of Texas - El Paso*

25.066-4. Beyond Boundaries: Comparative Explorations of Culture, Education, and Identities (Table 4). SIG-International Studies; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;

1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

- A Comparative Study on Preservice Teachers' Practicum Experiences in Korea and the U.S. *Gayoung Choi, University of Nebraska - Lincoln; HYOJUN YANG, Korea National University of Education*
- A Metaphorical Analysis of Teachers' Perceptions of Teaching in United States and China. *Leslie W. Grant, College of William & Mary; James H. Stronge, College of William & Mary; Swathi Menon, College of William & Mary*
- Preschool Teachers' Professional Learning in Taiwan and California. *ChingWen Huang, HUNGKUANG UNIVERSITY; Mei Wen Lai, Cardinal Tien Junior College of Healthcare and Management; Chu Hsi Tseng, San Francisco State University*
- Semantic Network Analysis of Early Childhood Curriculum from NYS (U.S.), BC (Canada), and South Korea. *Hyeseong Lee, Lewis University; Younsun Lee, Busan National University of Education; Hyeyoung Ghim, University of Missouri - Kansas City; Yeonghwi Ryu, Gwangju National University of Education*
- Chair: *Eman Abo-Zaed Arar, Texas State University*

25.066-5. Comparative Perspectives on Education and policy insights from a Chinese context (Table 5). SIG-International Studies; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

- A Comparative Study between Chinese and Indian International Students in United States Higher Education. *Lianzi Ouyang, University at Buffalo - SUNY*
- A Cross-Stage Comparative Study of Family and Peer Influence on Academic Self-Efficacy Among Chinese International Students in U.S. Higher Education. *Chang Wang, University of California - Santa Barbara*
- Learning and Living Under Political Scrutiny: Chinese International Students in the United States in an Era of Geopolitical Tensions and Political Hostility. *Xin Wang, Baylor University*
- Gendered Pathways and Precarious Promises: Chinese International Graduates Navigating the U.S. Temporary Visa Regime. *Yuejia Wang, University at Buffalo - SUNY*
- Chair: *Abdulrasheed Olatunji Abdussalam, Visiting Prof at McGill University*

25.066-6. Educational Leadership and Policy for Systemic Change (Table 6). SIG-Educational Change; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

- System Leadership and Education Change: Exploring the Evidence. *Alma Harris, Cardiff Metropolitan University;*

Michelle Suzette Jones, Cardiff Metropolitan University; Julia Longville, Cardiff Metropolitan University; Alan Gorman, Dublin City University; Fiona M. King, Dublin City University; Romina Madrid Miranda, University of Stirling

Leading School to Successful Change: A Meta-Synthesis of 20 Years of International Case Studies. *Junqi Lin, University of Alabama; Huaiyue Zhang, University of Alabama; Rong Zhang, University of Alabama; Ting Huang, University of Alabama*

Tracing Shifts in K–12 Education Research: A Topic Modeling Analysis of Publications from 1990-2023. *Amanda L. Datnow, University of California - San Diego; Yan Jiang, Stanford University; John Diaz, University of California - San Diego; Vicki Park, San Diego State University*

Chair: *Amanda L. Datnow, University of California - San Diego*
Discussant: *Thomas C. Hatch, Teachers College, Columbia University*

25.066-7. Black Feminism, Voice, and Hip Hop Praxis (Table 7). SIG-Hip Hop Theories, Praxis & Pedagogies; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

- Hip Hop Pedagogy and the #HotGirlSemester Accompaniment. *Qiana Cutts Givens, Mississippi State University*
- Magic, Alive: Afrofuturism and Black Feminism through the Works of McKinley Dixon and Little Simz. *Christian Michael Folk, University of Texas at Austin*
- We Out Here: Remixing Student Engagement via Black Women's Hip-Hop Narratives Featuring Rapsody's Album Eve. *Eghosa Obaizamomwan-Hamilton, Stanford University*
- Witness, Remember, Remix: Black Women Educators and the Transformative Praxis of the Cypher. *Romonda Middlebrooks-Jefferson, Georgia State University*
- Chair: *Hyacinth T Campbell, Brock University*

25.066-8. Empowered Voices: Rethinking and Reclaiming Pedagogy in Indigenous Contexts (Table 8). SIG-Indigenous Peoples of the Pacific and Beyond; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

- Teaching Through Story, Learning Through Life: A'ō and Ako as Indigenous Pedagogical Approaches. *Jerusha Nanea Puanani Magalei, Brigham Young University - Hawaii*
- Designing and Implementing Indigenous Knowledge Curricula: A Case Study of the Amis People in Taiwan. *HUI MIN CHOU, National Academy for Educational Research; Shu-Huei Yen, Rong-Shan AI Education Application and Promotion Association*
- Reducing Inequality in STEM Through Broadened

Participation. *Sharon Nelson-Barber, WestEd*
A Consideration of Artistic Expressions of Younger
Generations in Educational Setting. *Yuki Takatori, Toyo
University*

Chair: *Jeffrey Chun-Lum, University of Hawai'i at Mānoa*
Discussant: *Julie L. Kaomea, University of Hawai'i at Manoa*

**25.066-9. Beyond Metrics: Servingness, Linguistic Justice, and
Culturally Rooted Praxis in Higher Education (Table 9).**

SIG-Latina/o/x Research Issues; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Hispanic Students as Environmental Scientists: Culturally
Sustaining STEM Pathways Through Raíces y Ciencia. *Uma
Maheshwari Ganesan, University of Texas - Rio Grande
Valley*

Mentoring with a Mindful Approach among Latinx STEM
Faculty and Students at an HSI. *Hilda Cecilia Contreras
Aguirre, New Mexico State University; Maryanne Long,
University of Texas - El Paso; Luis Rodolfo Garcia Carrillo,
New Mexico State University*

More Than Enrollment: Examining Institutional Spaces,
Identity, and Mental Health at an HSI. *Amber Michelle
Gonzalez, California State University - Sacramento; Kevin
Ferreira van Leer, University of Connecticut; Maria
Guadalupe Razo-Soto, California State University -
Sacramento; Claudia L. Gonzalez, California State
University - Sacramento; Darlis Pantoja-Benavides,
University of Connecticut; Noah Sebastian Gomez,
California State University - Sacramento*

Reimagining Culturally-Affirming Spaces at Hispanic Serving
Institutions by Building on Students' Ventajas y
Conocimientos. *Lupita Romo-González, University of
California - Santa Barbara*

Translanguaging in Liderazgo: Linguistic Flexibility as
Servingness. *Margarita Anahi Rodriguez, University of
California - Santa Barbara; Lucy Arellano, University of
California - Santa Barbara; Carlos A Fitch, University of
California - Santa Barbara; Maritza Ordaz, University of
California - Santa Barbara; M. Magdalena Jimenez Aguilar,
University of California - Santa Barbara*

Chair: *Uma Maheshwari Ganesan, University of Texas - Rio
Grande Valley*

**25.067. AERA Roundtable Session Wednesday 1:45 pm - Gold
3; Roundtable Session**

**25.067-1. Being Queer and Trans on Campus: Leadership,
Campus Policies, and Cross-Cultural Mobilization
(Table 1).**

SIG-Queer Studies; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

From "Cultural Mismatch" to "Cross-Cultural Mobilization":
First-Generation LGBTQ+ College Students' Experiences,
Challenges, and Opportunities. *Ying-Chao Kao, Virginia
Commonwealth University; Yiwen Wei, Virginia
Commonwealth University; nicole killian, Virginia
Commonwealth University*

Queer and Trans Leadership: Advancing Equity and
Dismantling Cisheteronormativity in Higher Education.
*Gabriel Pulido, University of Wisconsin - LaCrosse; Sergio
A. Gonzalez, University of Pittsburgh*

Resistance and Retreat: Connecting Judicial and State Policy
Contexts to LGBTQ+ Affirming Campus Policy. *Travis
Heath Olson, Michigan State University; Ailidh Wallace,
College of William & Mary; Obed Amoakoh Boateng,
Virginia Commonwealth University; Kamden Strunk,
Virginia Commonwealth University; Amanda J. Davis
Simpfenderfer, College of William & Mary; Mario I Suárez,
Utah State University; Jason C. Garvey, University of
Vermont*

Transborder Fluidity: Identity Shifts and Spatial Belonging for
Queer and Trans Transfronterix Graduate Students. *Carlos
A Fitch, University of California - Santa Barbara*

**25.067-2. Leading Education at the Intersection of Queerness
and Transness: School Leaders, Embodiment, and
Transformation (Table 2).**

SIG-Queer Studies; Roundtable
Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Embodied: Finding Ways to Thrive as a Queer Non-Binary
Black Womxn K-12 Educator. *Whitney S. Hanley,
University of Kentucky*

Glitter and Shade: A Phenomenological Pilot Study on
LGBTQ+ School Leaders. *Patricia Kay Hanson, Claremont
Graduate University*

Queerly Inhabited Institutions: How LGBTQ School Leaders
Transform Inclusive K-12 Practices. *Anna Kushner,
Teachers College, Columbia University*

**25.067-3. Innovative Tools for Supporting Social Emotional
Learning (Table 3).**

SIG-Social and Emotional Learning;
Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Integrating RAG-Enhanced AI to Support Cognitive, Affective,
and Psychomotor Balance in K-12 Lesson Plans. *Shun-
Ching Hsieh, National Chengchi University 國立政治大學*

Neurodiverse Youth Book Clubs for Transformative and
Inclusive Social Emotional Learning. *Jody N. Polleck,
Hunter College - CUNY*

Revealing the Key Factors behind Academic and Social-
Emotional Resilience: A Machine Learning and IPTW

Approach. *Siyuan Chen, University of California - Santa Barbara; Xin Tang, Shanghai Jiao Tong University*

Chair: *Jeffrey Liew, Texas A&M University*

25.067-4. Civic Spaces: Seen, Unseen, and Waiting To Be Seen (Table 4). SIG-Social Studies Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Bearing Witness: Protecting Black History Within Black Nonfiction Picture Books. *Dawnayn James, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

“Eight Pounds of Air”: Centering Democracy and Civic Engagement Through Sport in Social Studies. *Alex E. Chisholm, Clemson University*

“Our Constitution is Colorblind”: A CRT Analysis of SCOTUS Cases in Secondary Social Studies Standards. *Joseph Adam Schultz, University of Georgia; Rebecca Cooper Geller, University of Georgia*

Racial Literacy, Capabilities, and Curriculum Making for Secondary Social Studies. *Kelly León, University of Wisconsin - Green Bay; David Lambert, University College London; Edward M. Olivos, University of Oregon*

“What Does Patriotism Look Like?”: Exploring National Identity Discourses in a Fifth Grade Classroom. *Seunghoon Han, University of Northern Iowa*

25.067-5. Family Matters: Parental Roles in Shaping Learning, Motivation, and Educational Pathways (Table 5).

Division C - Learning and Instruction; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Relations Between Parent Expectations and Youths’ Math Expectancies Through STEM Extracurriculars: Gender By College Generation Status. *Hyewon Lee, University of California - Irvine; Christy R. Starr, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Miranda G. Goldstein, University of California - Irvine; Jacquelynne S. Eccles, University of California - Irvine; Sandra D. Simpkins, University of California - Irvine*

Parental Multimodal Revoicing: Guiding Children in Computational Thinking Learning. *Grace Yaxin Xing, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

More Than Advocacy: A Qualitative Study of How Parents Regulate Belonging For Students With ASD. *Erica Ellsworth Miller, Washington University in St. Louis; Anna Freeman, Washington University in St. Louis; Wendy Chavez, Washington University in St. Louis; Amanda Plaxe, Washington University in St. Louis; Chris Rozek, Washington University in St. Louis*

Mothers, Fathers, and the Road to College in Latinx Families. *Madelyn H. Molina, Texas State University; So Yeon Lee, The University of Alabama at Birmingham; Yishan Shen, Texas State University; Edna C. Alfaro, Texas State*

University; Eunjin Seo, Texas State University

Chair: *Hyewon Lee, University of California - Irvine*

25.067-6. Explorations of identity and belonging in/through arts based educational research (Table 6). SIG-Arts-Based Educational Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Aesthetic Rhythms of Belonging. *Jeneca Parker-Tongue, Hunter College - CUNY*

(Re)Imagining Educational Futures for Refugees and Asylum-seekers: A Photovoice Study of Forced Displacement and Schooling. *Pempho Chinkondenji, University of North Dakota; Giovanni E. Whyte, University of North Dakota; Celine Mudahakana, University of Massachusetts - Amherst*

Staging Identity Through Fictionalized Drama. *Sundus Iftikhar, University of Alabama; Kelly W. Guyotte, University of Alabama*

Discussant: *Patience Amadu, University of Colorado - Colorado Springs*

25.067-7. Teaching in Complex Times: Spotlight on Teaching Motivation and Emotions (Table 7). SIG-Motivation in Education Cosponsored with Division C - Learning and Instruction; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Culture, Not Color: The Role of Perceived Similarity in Teacher Empathetic Motivations. *Joseph Eisman, Purdue University*

Investigating Teacher Anger, Emotional Labor of Anger, and Emotional Exhaustion from Two Daily Diary Studies. *Hui Wang, The Education University of Hong Kong; Ying Chen, The Education University of Hong Kong*

Motivations and Meaning-Making in Becoming a Social Studies Teacher: A Narrative Inquiry. *MG Hodge, Temple University; Alyssa Josselsohn, Temple University; Youngseo Kim, Temple University; Francisco Villa, Temple University; Abby Reisman, University of Pennsylvania; Timothy Patterson, Temple University; Avi Kaplan, Temple University*

Teaching While Targeted: Motivational Impacts of Anti-DEI Legislation on Aspiring Pre-Service Teachers of Color. *Xiao-Yin Chen, University of Tennessee; Patricia J. Higgins, University of Tennessee, Knoxville; Korinthia D. Nicolai, Indiana University; Francia Iszamar Zelaya Zapata, University of Tennessee; Michelle Bradley, University of Tennessee; Amber Rosamond, University of Tennessee*

Chair: *Kanvarbir Gill, University of Oklahoma*

25.067-8. Integrating Artificial Intelligence in Teaching and Learning (Table 8). SIG-Technology, Instruction,

Cognition & Learning; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

- AI Integration, Professional Development, and Instructional Quality in K-12 Education. *Marc Egloffstein, University of Mannheim; Nele Groß, Leuphana University - Lueneburg; Christopher Neil Prilop, Aarhus University; Dana-Kristin Mah, Leuphana University - Lueneburg*
- Introducing Artificial Intelligence into Vocational Curriculum Evaluation: Empirical Examination and Model Construction. *Tianjian WANG, Guangzhou University*
- Meta-Aggregation of Qualitative Evidence on Technology Integration in Teacher Education. *Afaq Ahmed, Texas A&M University; Andrew Kwok, Texas A&M University*
- Supporting Future-Ready Math Classrooms with ProductiveMath: A Web-based, Human-in-the-Loop Generative AI Tool. *Seyedahmad Rahimi, University of Florida; Maryam Babaee, University of Florida; Salah Esmailigoujar, University of Florida; Deniz Ercan, University of Florida; Ran Gao, University of Florida*
- Using Large Language Models to Analyze Technology Integration in K-12 Canadian Curricula. *Esther Yu, University of Toronto - OISE; Calpanaa Jegatheeswaran, University of Toronto; Sumayya Saleem, University of Toronto - OISE; Elizabeth Dhuey, University of Toronto - Scarborough; Michal Perlman*
- Chair: *Matthew Nyaaba, University of Georgia*

Division and SIG Posters

25.068. AERA Poster Session Wednesday 1:45pm; Poster Session

25.068-1. Exhausted but Effective? Teacher Burnout & Student Achievement in Chinese Middle Schools.

Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 1:45-3:15pm

Poster:

1. Exhausted but Effective? A Study of Teacher Burnout and Student Achievement in Chinese Middle Schools (Poster 1). *Feifan Shan, University of Pennsylvania*

25.068-2. Confucianism, Buddhism and Taoism in Education.

SIG-Confucianism, Taoism, Buddhism and Education;
Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 1:45-3:15pm

Posters:

2. Contemplative Environmental Education Across Traditions: Rekindling Love for Nature in Pakistan, China, and Beyond

- (Poster 2). *Maha Shoaib, University of Maryland; Jing Lin, University of Maryland; Yueyue Wang, University of Maryland; Denise L. McHugh, University of Maryland*
3. Does Educational Anxiety Inhibit Fertility Intention? An Empirical Study Based on CFPS (Poster 3). *Kaiwei Zhang, East China Normal University; Feng Zhang, East China Normal University; Li Liu, East China Normal University; Lili Liu, East China Normal University*
4. “Less Is More”: Taoist Perspective to Rethink Extending Culturally Relevant Pedagogy to (International) Higher Education (Poster 4). *Wenjin Guo, Xi'an University of Architecture and Technology; Siyuan Gong, Chang'an University*
5. Micromomentary Mindset towards Anticolonial Intentionality (Poster 5). *Sultan Turkan, Queen's University - Belfast; Mel M. Engman, Queen's University - Belfast*
6. The Humility/Confidence Paradox in Education (Poster 6). *Liz Jackson, University of Hong Kong*

25.068-3. Data-Driven Decision Making in Education SIG Poster Session. SIG-Data-Driven Decision Making in Education; Poster Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 1:45-3:15pm

Posters:

7. Shift Happens: Tracing COVID's Impact on 2017-2018 Fourth Graders Across States Over Four Years (Poster 7). *Vinh Quang Tran, St. John's University; Gulnur Ozbek, St. John's University*
8. Predictors of Student Performance in HyFlex Environment: Insights from multilevel modeling (Poster 8). *Elnara Mammadova, Purdue University; Michel Cordoba, Purdue University; Nathan Mentzer, Purdue University*
9. Predictive Modeling of COVID-19 Math Learning Loss Using Educational Data Mining and Longitudinal Growth Trajectories (Poster 9). *Zhuoying Wang, University of Texas at Austin; Shifang Tang, East Texas A&M University; David Daniel Jimenez, Texas A&M University - Corpus Christi; Mei Jiang, East Texas A&M University; Lei Zhang, East Texas A&M University*

25.068-4. Supporting Sensemaking in Science Teaching and Learning. SIG-Science Teaching and Learning; Poster Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 1:45-3:15pm

Posters:

10. Building Pathways to Success: Effective Interventions for Undergraduate STEM Student Persistence (Poster 10). *Marisa E. Castellano, WestEd; Andrew Grillo-Hill, WestEd; Pai-Rou Chen, WestEd*
11. Early STEM in and out of the classroom: Perspectives from Parents and other Caregivers (Poster 11). *Emily Anne Lyons, Springfield College*

12. Framing Towards Culturally Relevant Practice in Nigerian Physics Education (Poster 12). *Lucky Chukwudalu Nonyelum, Create for Stem Institute; Clausell Mathis, Michigan State University; Ozlem Akcil Okan, Michigan State University; Mathilda Smith, Michigan State University*
13. Heteroglossia and Heterogeneity: A Critical Discourse Analysis of a Chinese Newcomer Student Making Sense of Energy Transfer and Transformation (Poster 13). *Zhenjie Hou, University of Houston; Jie Zhang, University of Houston*
14. Investigating the population-dependent characteristic and transitional process of learning progression using model analysis: A case study of force and motion (Poster 14). *YI DING, Nanjing University Of Information and Science Technology*
15. Kindergarten Teachers' Commitment to Science Teaching: Conceptualization and Measurement (Poster 15). *Wen Qi, University of Hong Kong; Li-Fang Zhang, University of Hong Kong; Qingsong Zhao, Hefei Preschool Education College*
16. Navigating Online Physics: Barriers, Enablers, and Integrity Concerns Among Non-Traditional Adult Learners (Poster 16). *Jude Sullivan, Pennsylvania State University; Ashlyn Leary, Lehigh University; J. Bryan Henderson, Arizona State University; Molly Simon, Arizona State University; Louis Leblond, Pennsylvania State University*
17. Reducing Psychosocial Gaps of Freshman Science and Mathematics Majors through a Structured First-Year Seminar Course (Poster 17). *Supuni Dhameera Silva, Louisiana State University; Zakiya S. Wilson-Kennedy, Louisiana State University*
18. Science Writing Interventions and Student Achievement: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis (Poster 18). *Hanyue Sha, University of Texas at Austin; Doris Luft Baker, University of Texas at Austin; Chi Ma, University of Texas at Austin; Peng Peng, University of Texas at Austin*
19. Sensemaking in the System: Understanding Local Variability in Science Standards Implementation (Poster 19). *Kathryn M. Bateman, Pennsylvania State University - Harrisburg; Amy E Long, Lock Haven University*
20. The Effects of Learning Sequence on Students' Understanding of the Particulate Nature of Matter (Poster 20). *Jiaojiao Hui, The University of Hong Kong*
21. Virtual Simulations for Quantitative Sensemaking in Elementary Science (Poster 21). *Joelle Prate, Chapman University*
22. Zooming in on Socio-Scientific Issues: Exploring Science and Social Studies Integration with Preservice Teachers (Poster 22). *Soo Won Shim, Illinois State University; Xiaoying Zhao, Illinois State University; Sung Eun Jung, University of Arizona*
23. Exploring the Sources and Development of Self-Efficacy Among Teachers Implementing a Middle School Engineering Curriculum (Poster 23). *Jessica Gale, Georgia Institute of Technology; Sunni Newton, Georgia Institute of*

Technology; Meltem Alemdar, Georgia Institute of Technology; Dyanne Baptiste Porter, Georgia Institute of Technology; Jasmine Sookhyun Choi, Georgia Institute of Technology

25.068-5. Contemporary Issues in Online Instruction and Student Learning. SIG-Online Teaching and Learning; Poster Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 1:45-3:15pm

Posters:

24. Beyond Constraints: Constructing a New Vision for Advisors Supporting Residential Undergraduate Students in Asynchronous Courses (Poster 24). *Michelle Mondrey, Morgan State University; Virginia Byrne, Morgan State University; Christine Licata-Hoang, Morgan State University; Adeoluwa Oluwatoyin Folami, Morgan State University*
25. Career Exploration in Online Data Science Education: A Curriculum Analytics Approach (Poster 25). *Daniela Castellanos-Reyes, North Carolina State University; Tom R. Leppard, North Carolina State University*
26. Following Through on Intention: How Learner Personas Influence MOOC Completion and Performance (Poster 26). *Rob Moore, University of Florida; Chuang Wang, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Sophia Soomin Lee, University of Florida*
27. LLM-Generated Knowledge Graphs for Analyzing the Association between Student Participation and Learning in Online Math Discussions (Poster 27). *Chenglu Li, University of Utah; Bailing Lyu, University of Utah; Gokhan Gulfidan, University of Utah; Linlin Wu, University of Utah; Rui Guo, University of Florida*
28. Relevance of Instructional Design Modeling Support in Online Instruction: Faculty or AI? (Poster 28). *Yingying Liu, Towson University; Cherrng-Jyh Yen, Old Dominion University; Chih-Hsiung Tu, Northern Arizona University; Hoda Harati, Towson University; Mahnaz Moallem, Towson University; Patricia J. Peterson, Northern Arizona University*
29. Scaling Success: Barriers and Supports for Completion of a Statewide Early Literacy Micro-Credential (Poster 29). *Sophia Soomin Lee, University of Florida; Danielle Pico, University of Florida; Julianna Banks, University of Florida; Concepción Moncada Cummings, University of Florida; Mary Bratsch-Hines, University of Florida; Maria Virginia Giani, University of Florida; Tia Walton-Walker, University of Florida; Tyran Butler, University of Florida*
30. Shifting the Narrative in MOOC Research: Insights from Volunteer Evaluators Using a Learning Analytics Approach (Poster 30). *Songhee Han, Florida State University; Daniela Castellanos-Reyes, North Carolina State University; Zilu Jiang, Johns Hopkins University*
31. Talent Development, University-Based Summer Camps,

Classroom Quality, and Online Versus In-Person Learning Post-COVID-19 (Poster 31). *Hernan Castillo-Hermosilla, Purdue University; Nielsen Pereira, Purdue University/Gifted Education Research & Resource Institute*

32. Comparing Online Learning Readiness Across Educational Stages in Taiwan: Elementary to Senior High (Poster 32). *Chien Chou, National Yang Ming Chiao Tung University; Min-Ling Hung, Ming Chuan University; Zoe Ruo-Yu Li, University College London - IOE*

33. Rethinking Pre-Class Modality in Flipped Learning: A Comparative Study of Textbook Reading and Instructor-Created Videos (Poster 33). *Eunbae Lee, Kyung Hee University; Jackie HeeYoung Kim, Georgia Southern University; Moon-Heum Cho, Syracuse University; Seongmi Lim, Ball State University*

25.068-6. Black Post-Secondary Student Experience, Data, and Belonging Across Educational Spaces. SIG-Research Focus on Black Education; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 1:45-3:15pm

Posters:

34. An Afropessimist Examination of Black Undergraduates' Experiences in the Afterlife of School Segregation (Poster 34). *Alex J. Kenney, Rutgers University*

35. Culturally Relevant Data Science Analytics, Student Motivation, and Learning at an HBCU (Poster 35). *Monica B. Mitchell, MERAssociates; LaTanya Brown-Robertson, Howard University; Amy Quarkume, Howard University; Andrea Calloway, Howard University*

36. "Going Somewhere in Life" (Poster 36). *April Claytor, School District of Philadelphia*

37. Invisible and Undervalued: How College Students Perceive Privilege and the Positioning of Black Women (Poster 37). *Franklin Dickerson Turner, Kean University; Zuri Gill, Kean University*

38. Mentoring for Justice and Joy: Undergraduate Experiences in a Central California Collaborative Project (Poster 38). *Swati Mehta, California State University - Fresno; Patricia Lane, California State University - Fresno; Randy Yerrick, California State University - Fresno; Patrick S De Walt, California State University - Fresno*

25.068-7. Contemporary Discussions in Learning Environments 2. SIG-Learning Environments; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 1:45-3:15pm

Posters:

39. An Agentic Framework for Informal Digital Spaces within STEM (Poster 39). *Grace L. Tukurah, Michigan State University; Muhammad Zulqurnain Ul Haq Qazi, The Ohio State University; Hawanya Smith, University of California - Davis*

40. Craft with Oki Pie: A Tool for Brainstorming Contextual Project Ideas in Children's Makerspaces (Poster 40). *Sonia Tiwari, Kids AI*

41. What legitimises teacher's authority? Validation of a scale based on students' perspectives (Poster 41). *Guillermo Manuel Zamora Poblete, Pontificia Universidad Catolica de Chile; Marisa Meza Pardo, Pontificia Universidad Catolica de Chile; Pilar Cox, Pontificia Universidad Catolica de Chile; Camila Ortiz, universidad de santiago de chile*

25.068-8. Black Women Healthcare Employees' Perspectives on Organizational Justice. SIG-Research on Women and Education; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 1:45-3:15pm

Posters:

42. Bi Nka Bi: Black Women's Perspective's on Organizational Justice as Healthcare Employees (Poster 42). *Cecilia Noelle Vaughn-Guy, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

25.068-9. School Community, Climate, and Culture SIG Posters. SIG-School Community, Climate, and Culture; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 1:45-3:15pm

Posters:

43. Transforming the Culture of Professional Learning Community through Lesson Study: An Activity Theory Perspective (Poster 43). *Zheng Xin, East China Normal University; Xiu Zhou, Southwest University*

44. Understanding the Contextual Impact of Leadership of Teaching-Research Team Leaders on Professional Learning Communities: The Role of Interpersonal Trust, Relational Conflict, and Confucian Traditional Values (Poster 44). *Yun Qu, Beihang University; Fei Wang, Beihang University*

45. Unpacking the Pathways: Self-Efficacy, Learning Activities, and Socioeconomic Disparities in Students' Global Competence (Poster 45). *Jiang Yuxiao, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Qinhuai Huang, Beijing Normal University*

25.068-10. Centering Wellness and Reimagining a Future for Educational Leadership. SIG-Leadership for Social Justice; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 1:45-3:15pm

Posters:

46. Reimagining Their Future: Lessons Learned for Women of Color in Educational Leadership Positions (Poster 46). *Ronald Dennis Morgan, National University; Kitty M. Fortner, California State University - Dominguez Hills; Kimmie Tang, Alder Graduate School of Education*

47. Centering Wellness for Justice: The Role of Resilient Principals in Mandarin Dual Language Immersion

Leadership (Poster 47). *Natasha Neumann, California Polytechnic State University - San Luis Obispo; Soomin Chao, California State University - Fullerton*

25.068-11. Poster Session II -- AERA Division D Section 1: Measurement, Psychometrics, and Assessment. Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 1:45-3:15pm

Posters:

48. A Review of Equity Indicators; What are we Actually Measuring? (Poster 48). *Courtney Donovan, University of Colorado - Denver; Angela Rexwinkle, University of Colorado - Denver; Abbey Eversole, University of Colorado - Denver; Abigail B. Rose, University of Denver; Rachel N. Robinson, University of Colorado - Denver; Emilie Waggoner, University of Colorado - Denver*
49. Development of a Game-Bases Assessment to Thinking Style (Poster 49). *Xinyu Liu, Beijing Normal University; Tianqi Wu, Beijing Normal University; Ruofan zhang, Beijing Normal University; Yinghui Tang, Beijing Normal University; Yingshi Xu, Beijing Normal University*
50. Hybrid Models for DIF Detection: A Simulation Study of Classical and Machine Learning Approaches (Poster 50). *Mohammad Jahanaray, Virginia Commonwealth University; Atena Pasha, University of South Carolina*
51. Impact of Position on the Response Speed and Accuracy of Scenario Items (Poster 51). *Yi Lu, The Federation of State Boards of Physical Therapy; Yu Zhang, The Federation of State Boards of Physical Therapy; Lorin Mueller, Federation of State Boards of Physical Therapy*
52. Psychometric properties of the Arabic Version of Parental Burnout Assessment in Qatar (Poster 52). *Elsayed Elshabrawi A. Hassanein, Qatar University*
53. Revisiting the Self-Report Altruism Scale in Higher Education: Rasch-Based Cross-Cultural Validation and Refinement. (Poster 53). *Talal Alzabidi, University of North Carolina Greensboro; Reben Ramadhan Ramadhan Saleh, Lobachevsky State University*
54. Human-AI Co-Grading of Open-Ended Responses to STEM Transfer Questions (Poster 54). *Xinyue Jiao, New York University; Basel Hussein, New York University; Yuli Shao, New York University; Yuqi Hang, New York University; Alvaro Olsen, New York University; Jan L. Plass, New York University*
55. A K-12 Testing Program's Journey of Hybrid Automated and Manual Test Assembly (Poster 55). *Su Zhang, Ontario Education Quality and Accountability Office; Jennifer Hove, Education Quality and Accountability Office; Zhimei Gu, Education Quality and Accountability Office*

25.068-12. Learning Sciences Poster Session 2. SIG-Learning Sciences; Poster Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 1:45-3:15pm

Poster:

56. Near-peer Mentors' Experiences Facilitating Co-design Activities with Black and Brown Boys using Emerging Technologies (Poster 56). *Elana B Blinder, University of Maryland; Akhil Gurram, University of Pennsylvania; Brian Gardner, University of Maryland; Clayton Felder, University of Maryland - Baltimore County; Isaiah Harris, Prince George's Community College; Tamara L. Clegg, University of Maryland; Elizabeth Bonsignore, University of Maryland*

25.069. e-Lightning Ed-Talk Session 4 - Stage 1. AERA e-Lightning Ed-Talks; AERA Ed Talk

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Exhibit Hall A - Stage 1; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

- Impact of Position on the Response Speed and Accuracy of Scenario Items (Stage 1, 1:50 PM). *Yi Lu, The Federation of State Boards of Physical Therapy; Yu Zhang, The Federation of State Boards of Physical Therapy; Lorin Mueller, Federation of State Boards of Physical Therapy*
 - Hybrid Models for DIF Detection: A Simulation Study of Classical and Machine Learning Approaches (Stage 1, 1:59 PM). *Mohammad Jahanaray, Virginia Commonwealth University; Atena Pasha, University of South Carolina*
 - Diagnosing Spatial and Executive Skills in XR Vocational Training With Cognitive Diagnosis (Stage 1, 2:08 PM). *Sae Hyun Park, New York University; Sangbeak Ye, Florida Atlantic University; Ayse Torres, Florida Atlantic University*
 - Human-AI Co-Grading of Open-Ended Responses to STEM Transfer Questions (Stage 1, 2:17 PM). *Xinyue Jiao, New York University; Basel Hussein, New York University; Yuli Shao, New York University; Yuqi Hang, New York University; Alvaro Olsen, New York University; Jan L. Plass, New York University*
 - "Less Is More": Taoist Perspective to Rethink Extending Culturally Relevant Pedagogy to (International) Higher Education (Stage 1, 2:26 PM). *Wenjin Guo, Xi'an University of Architecture and Technology; Siyuan Gong, Chang'an University*
 - Does Educational Anxiety Inhibit Fertility Intention? An Empirical Study Based on CFPS (Stage 1, 2:35 PM). *Kaiwei Zhang, East China Normal University; Feng Zhang, East China Normal University; Li Liu, East China Normal University; Lili Liu, East China Normal University*
 - Contemplative Environmental Education Across Traditions: Rekindling Love for Nature in Pakistan, China, and Beyond (Stage 1, 2:50 PM). *Maha Shoaib, University of Maryland; Jing Lin, University of Maryland; Yueyue Wang, University of Maryland; Denise L. McHugh, University of Maryland*
- Chair: *Jerome V. D'Agostino, The Ohio State University*

25.070. e-Lightning Ed-Talk Session 4 - Stage 2. AERA e-Lightning Ed-Talks; AERA Ed Talk
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Exhibit Hall A
- Stage 2; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Centering Wellness for Justice: The Role of Resilient Principals in Mandarin Dual Language Immersion Leadership (Stage 2, 1:50 PM). *Natasha Neumann, California Polytechnic State University - San Luis Obispo; Soomin Chao, California State University - Fullerton*

Craft with Oki Pie: A Tool for Brainstorming Contextual Project Ideas in Children's Makerspaces (Stage 2, 1:59 PM). *Sonia Tiwari, Kids AI*

Beyond Constraints: Constructing a New Vision for Advisors Supporting Residential Undergraduate Students in Asynchronous Courses (Stage 2, 2:08 PM). *Michelle Mondrey, Morgan State University; Virginia Byrne, Morgan State University; Christine Licata-Hoang, Morgan State University; Adeoluwa Oluwatoyin Folami, Morgan State University*

An Afropessimist Examination of Black Undergraduates' Experiences in the Afterlife of School Segregation (Stage 2, 2:17 PM). *Alex J. Kenney, Rutgers University*

Culturally Relevant Data Science Analytics, Student Motivation, and Learning at an HBCU (Stage 2, 2:26 PM). *Monica B. Mitchell, MERAssociates; LaTanya Brown-Robertson, Howard University; Amy Quarkume, Howard University; Andrea Calloway, Howard University*

"Going Somewhere in Life" (Stage 2, 2:35 PM). *April Claytor, School District of Philadelphia*

Mentoring for Justice and Joy: Undergraduate Experiences in a Central California Collaborative Project (Stage 2, 2:44 PM). *Swati Mehta, California State University - Fresno; Patricia Lane, California State University - Fresno; Randy Yerrick, California State University - Fresno; Patrick S De Walt, California State University - Fresno*

Chair: *Vaughn W.M. Watson, Michigan State University*

25.071. e-Lightning Ed-Talk Session 4 - Stage 3. AERA e-Lightning Ed-Talks; AERA Ed Talk
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Exhibit Hall A
- Stage 3; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Shift Happens: Tracing COVID's Impact on 2017-2018 Fourth Graders Across States Over Four Years (Stage 3, 1:50 PM). *Vinh Quang Tran, St. John's University; Gulnur Ozbek, St. John's University*

Predictors of Student Performance in HyFlex Environment: Insights from multilevel modeling (Stage 3, 1:59 PM). *Elnara Mammadova, Purdue University; Michel Cordoba, Purdue University; Nathan Mentzer, Purdue University*

Science Writing Interventions and Student Achievement: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis (Stage 3, 2:08 PM). *Hanyue Sha, University of Texas at Austin; Doris Luft*

Baker, University of Texas at Austin; Chi Ma, University of Texas at Austin; Peng Peng, University of Texas at Austin
Reducing Psychosocial Gaps of Freshman Science and Mathematics Majors through a Structured First-Year Seminar Course (Stage 3, 2:17 PM). *Supuni Dhameera Silva, Louisiana State University; Zakiya S. Wilson-Kennedy, Louisiana State University*
Early STEM in and out of the classroom: Perspectives from Parents and other Caregivers (Stage 3, 2:26 PM). *Emily Anne Lyons, Springfield College*
Building Pathways to Success: Effective Interventions for Undergraduate STEM Student Persistence (Stage 3, 2:35 PM). *Marisa E. Castellano, WestEd; Andrew Grillo-Hill, WestEd; Pai-Rou Chen, WestEd*

Uncategorized Sessions

25.072. AERA Research in Progress Roundtable Session One. AERA Sessions; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
1:45-3:15pm

25.072. Research-in-Progress RT005 (Wednesday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Communal Healing: Art as a Third Space for Love. *Iyana Shanel Hill, The Ohio State University*

Filming Freedom: Arts-Based Pathways Methodology for Abolition in Education. *Dion K. Crommarty, Washington State University*

Manifesting the Village: Black Othermothering, Arts-Based Interventions, and Curriculum Building Toward Educator Capability. *K. Lynn Robinson, The Ohio State University*

Chair: *Gerald Campano, University of Pennsylvania*

25.072. Research-in-Progress RT008 (Wednesday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

In-Between Strangeness and Sensibility: School as Encounter. *Sulamita Inácio Freire, Universidade do Estado do Rio de Janeiro*

Integrating Math into Elementary Health Education: An Experimental Study. *Liyan Tang, Georgia State University; Xiaolu Liu, Georgia State University*

The Math Major Experience: United in Year One. *Melissa Soto, Claremont Graduate University*

Chair: *Sarah Lubienski, Indiana University*

25.072. Research-in-Progress RT011 (Wednesday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Efficacy and Feasibility of a Culturally Adapted Mindfulness-based Program for College Students in China: A Pilot Randomized Trial. *Cody Abbey, Stanford University*

Scholar-Caregivers and Perinatal Mental Health: Futuring Equitable Higher Education. *Alice Blecker, New York University; Shana E. DeVlieger, NYU; Ellen Keefe, New York University; Robin Neuhaus, New York University; Erin E. O'Connor, New York University*

Core Features and Longitudinal Pathways Between Positive Future Thinking and Depression. *Yuancheng Wu, University of Minnesota; Haoran Li, University of Minnesota; Juzhe Xi, East China Normal University*

Chair: *Mary Helen Immordino-Yang, University of Southern California*

25.072. Research-in-Progress RT015 (Wednesday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Designing an Infant-Toddler Hub in a Public High School: Gathering Feedback through Participatory Action Research. *Canequia Moulder, Oakland University; Krysti Jones, Oakland University; Taylor Fowlkes, Oakland University*

Examining the Early Math Education Landscape in California's Transitional Kindergarten. *Jetta McPhee, University of California - Berkeley; Dana Miller-Cotto, University of California - Berkeley*

Exploring the Compatibility of Social-Emotional Learning and Trauma-Informed Practice for Early Elementary Teachers. *Madzy LaMonica, Pennsylvania State University*

Story Creation in an Early Childhood Literacy Classroom. *Maile M. Newberry-Wortham, University of Missouri*

Taking myself off the pedestal: An Ethnographic Consideration of the Culturally Responsive Teaching Practices of an Early Elementary Teacher Candidate. *Elizabeth J. Norman, University of Massachusetts - Amherst*

Chair: *Carlton J. Fong, Texas State University*

25.072. Research-in-Progress RT021 (Wednesday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

"Don't Change (My Story) Unless ...": Relational Possibilities of GAI Chatbots in Reflective Writing. *Jusil Lee, Pennsylvania State University; Xingxing Xie, Pennsylvania State University*

Exploring feedback engagement in AI-assisted EFL writing

instruction. *Yangyang Yu, Shanghai Jiao Tong University*
Learning to Prompt, Prompting to Learn: Novice Programmers' Self-Regulated Learning with GenAI. *Shumin Zhao, University of Nevada - Reno*

Chair: *James W. Stigler, University of California - Los Angeles*

25.072. Research-in-Progress RT029 (Wednesday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

A Phenomenological Study of the Lived Mentoring Experiences of Black Women Faculty at HBCUs. *Leona McGowan, Elizabeth City State University*

Exploring the Mentorship Experiences of Black Female Undergraduate Students at a Predominantly White Institution. *Onyebuchi Stephanie Ewa, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

When Some Mentors Aren't Human: Expanding How We Understand Mentorship and Professional Support for Educators. *Edith P. Middleton, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Chair: *Angela Calabrese, University of Michigan*

25.072. Research-in-Progress RT038 (Wednesday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Examining Nature of Science Portrayal in Science Museum Exhibits Using the Families of Resemblance Approach. *Rachel Byard Garcia, Ohio University*

Good Science or Going Viral? Genetics Education on TikTok. *John P Burrell, University of Connecticut; Allison Hellman, Syracuse University*

"I'm just curious... does the teacher speak Spanish?": Teachers' Sensemaking about teaching Bi/Multilingual Learners. *Khadija Zogheib, Florida State University*

25.072. Research-in-Progress RT044 (Wednesday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Exploring Teacher Leadership Practices in Nigerian Secondary Schools. *Rosheedat Adeniji, University of Manitoba*

Program Coherence and Preparedness: Texas Novice Teachers' Perceptions of Educator Preparation Effectiveness. *Hannah Chalk, Baylor University*

Why is Their Desk Outside The Classroom? :Teacher Perceptions and Implicit Bias toward Black Students with EBD. *Master Brown, Pennsylvania State University*

Teaching with Cariño: Exploring Teachers' Perceptions of Marginalized Students and Instructional Practices. *Claudia*

Ramirez, Claremont Graduate University
Chair: Frank C. Worrell, University of California - Berkeley

25.072. Research-in-Progress RT045 (Wednesday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

In English, please! Exploring Translanguaging and Language Ideologies in a Kazakhstani International School. *Nursultan Assylov, UMass Amherst*

Labor of Love: Exploring Spanish-Language Professional Learning as a Site for Healing, Advocacy, and Bilingual Educator Resilience. *Ivette Marlenne Alvarez, Erikson Institute*

“Those Students Are Sequestered”: Kansas Secondary ELA Teachers’ Perspectives on ELL Support and Programming. *Génesis Aguilar Chávez, Kansas State University*

Chair: Ruth María López, University of Arizona

25.072. Research-in-Progress RT049 (Wednesday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Staying or Leaving? Teacher Turnover and Retention After Adoption of Head Start 2024 Compensation Policy. *Boyun Kim, Oakland University*

Teacher Burnout: A Quantitative Study on Teacher Assignment Structure. *Elizabeth Heckathorn, California State University - Bakersfield*

Understanding Well-Being: Weaving the Wisdom of Elementary Teachers of Color. *Nallely Beulah Aceves Romero, Stanford University*

Chair: David M. Osher, Education Collaboratory at Yale University

25.072. Research-in-Progress RT052 (Wednesday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Borrowing from a Future: Kuwento as Speculative Fiction. *Rochelle Zuniga, Florida International University*

English as Linguistic Capital and Pathway to Global Citizenship. *BENJAMIN FRANCIS PELLEGRINO, University of Nevada, Reno*

Imagining as a Collective: A Speculative Worldbuilding Approach to Moderation and Engagement in a Youth-Centered Digital Writing Community. *Louisa Dewey, University of Pennsylvania; Sunny Ajitabh, Rutgers University; Mary Wolters, University of Pennsylvania; Sophia Yao, University of Pennsylvania*

Portfolio Partners: Collaborative Writing Practices among

Online Elementary Education Students. *Amy Levin Plattner, Kansas State University*

Chair: Darnel Degand, University of California - Davis

25.072. Research-in-Progress RT056 (Wednesday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

“Invisible Newcomers”: First-Generation Burmese Refugee Students Life After High School. *Ngo Hna, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

Language Matching as Care: Educator Relationships and Newcomer Immigrant Youth. *Sebastian Lopez-Padilla, University of California - Santa Barbara; Carolyn Sattin-Bajaj, University of California - Santa Barbara*

Language Policy of Indonesian immigrant households living in the Midwest United States. *Prawita Simanjuntak, Michigan State University*

Mapping Indigenous-Sustaining Leadership in State Education Policy. *Torye Wren Banura, Michigan State University*

Chair: Jaekyung Lee, University at Buffalo - SUNY

25.072. Research-in-Progress RT067 (Wednesday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Examining How Gamification Shapes Engagement in Online Learning from Instructors’ Perspectives. *Chen Meng, Indiana University*

Fostering Engaging and Psychologically Safe Language Learning Environments: Integrating AI-Embedded VR into Informal Language Learning. *Eunkyong Elaine Cha, University of Georgia; Zheyang Zhu, University of Georgia; Theodore J. Kopcha, University of Georgia*

Policy and Practice: How Technology Guidelines Influence Teaching Practices and Student Engagement in Catholic Schools. *Jennifer Badzek, Marshall University*

Chair: Xiaoxia A. Newton, University of North Carolina - Charlotte

25.072. Research-in-Progress RT069 (Wednesday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Acceleration in Literacy Learning: A Phenomenological Study. *Anne Sudmeier, University of Wyoming*

A Systematic Literature Review of the Development and Implementation of AI-assisted Interventions for Anxiety. *Jingyi Yang, University of Georgia*

Summer Literacy Interventions and Student Attitudes Toward Reading. *Rory Cantwell, Virginia Commonwealth*

University; Jenny M Martin, Bridgewater College
Chair: Nicole Patton-Terry, Florida State University

25.072. Research-in-Progress RT077 (Wednesday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Responsive Coaching and School Improvement: How K-12 Principals and Their Coaches Set and Pursue Goals. *Jenna Nichols, University of Pennsylvania; Jonathan A. Supovitz, University of Pennsylvania*

"You Good?": Reflective Lifeguarding and the Black Principal's Commitment to Black Student Success. *Brittany Davis, Georgia State University; Sarah E. Carlson, Georgia State University*

How Principals Inspire Teachers: The Mediating Role of Informal Learning in Building Self-Efficacy for Student Engagement. *Kosar Shirzad, The Pennsylvania State University; Masoumeh Kouhsari; Brian R. Belland, Pennsylvania State University*

Chair: *Steven M. Sanders, Oregon State University*

25.072. Research-in-Progress RT078 (Wednesday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Authoring Counternarratives: A strategy to persist in science for Undergraduate women of color biology majors. *Carol Umanzor, University of Michigan*

Reexamining Relevance: A Discourse Analysis of Basic Science in Medical Education. *Tracy Boswell Fulton, University of California - San Francisco; Anika Dhingra, University of California San Francisco; Anna MacLeod, Dalhousie University; Marieke Van der Schaaf, University Medical Centre Utrecht; Bridget Colleen O'Brien, University of California - San Francisco*

#ThrivingInScienceWhileBlack: A New Framework for Understanding Black College Students Experiences with Thriving. *Analisa Brown, University of California - Davis*

Chair: *Sylvia Hurtado, University of California - Los Angeles*

Wednesday, April 8th, 3:45 pm

Governance Meetings and Events

26.001. AERA Council of Editors Meeting: Closed Meeting.
AERA Governance; Governance Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 518;
3:45-5:15pm

Chair: *John Neikirk, American Educational Research Association*

Presidential Sessions

26.010. Freedom-Making in the Now: A Fireside Chat on Critical Challenges to Carcerality in K-16 Education.
AERA Presidential Session; Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 406AB;
3:45-5:15pm

Chairs: *Keisha L. Green, University of Massachusetts - Amherst; Erica R. Meiners, Northeastern Illinois University*

Participants: *Julissa Muniz, University of California - Los Angeles; Roger Chung, Laney College; Miguel Casar, University of Alabama; Erin L. Castro, University of Utah; Brian Cabral, University of Texas at Austin; Niki Martinez, Sister Warriors Freedom Coalition*

Discussant: *Robin D. G. Kelley, University of California - Los Angeles*

Honorary President Edmund W. Gordon Series

26.011. Advancing Assessment in the Service of Learning.
AERA Honorary President Edmund W. Gordon Series;
Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 403B;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants: *Kadriye Ercikan, Educational Testing Service; Alina A. Von Davier, Duolingo; Edmund W. Gordon, Teachers College, Columbia University; James W. Pellegrino, University of Illinois at Chicago; Stephen G. Sireci, University of Massachusetts - Amherst*

Moderator: *Eric Tucker, The Study Group*

Committee Sessions

26.012. Division C Fireside Chat: It's the Little Things: Intentional Partnerships with K-12 Schools in Research.

Graduate Student Council Cosponsored with Division C - Learning and Instruction; Invited Speaker Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 402A;
3:45-5:15pm

Chairs: *Micaha Dean Hughes, North Carolina State University; Rebecca Myers, Montclair State University*

Panelists: *Mesmin Destin, Northwestern University; Laura P. Wentworth, California Education Partners; Michael C. Ralph, Multistudio; Samuela Mouzaour, Ingham Independent School District*

Division Sessions

26.013. Pathways and Promise: The Struggles, Triumphs, and Everything In Between of Female Superintendents of Color. Division A - Administration; Symposium

Westin Bonaventure, Level 2, Mt. Washington; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Leading While Black and Female: Factors to a Successful Career Pathway into the Superintendency. *Katie Russell, Panama-Buena Vista Union School District*

Rooted in Faith: Latina Educational Leaders' Use of Spiritual Capital as a Vital Resource. *Susan Gándara Rowley, Covina-Unified School District*

Female Superintendents of Color: Perspectives on Mentoring. *Teanya Bishop, Alvord Unified School District*

Aspirations: Systemic Influences on Women of Color's Desire to Pursue the Superintendency. *Dalia Gadalmawla, Corona-Norco Unified School District*

Chair: *Stacy Kula, Azusa Pacific University*

Discussant: *Stacy Kula, Azusa Pacific University*

26.014. Thinking, Planning, and Evaluating: The Use of Primary and Secondary Data to Improve Schools and Districts. Division A - Administration; Paper Session

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Los Feliz; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

District Network: Co-Imagining and Co-Creating District Futurities. *Vidya Shah, OISE/University of Toronto; Palvi Sidana, University of Toronto - OISE*

Reframing Improvement Mindset in Schools: Learning from Short-Cycle Planning in Chile. *Isabel Zett, Pontificia Universidad Catolica de Valparaiso; Felipe Aravena, Pontificia Universidad Catolica de Valparaiso; Coby Meyers, University of Virginia; Monica Cortez, Pontificia Universidad Catolica de Valparaiso; Macarena González-Murgas, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Valparaiso*

Middle-Level Inspection: Evaluating inspections to Local Public Education Services in Chile. *Xavier Vanni, Universidad de Chile; María Fernanda Goñi, CIAE Universidad de Chile*

A Qualitative Analysis to Understand Measurability of Goals and Action Steps in School Improvement Plans (SIPs). *Durga Kumar Karki, University of Delaware; Bryan A. VanGronigen, University of Delaware*

Chair: *Matthew S. McCluskey, University of Vermont*

Discussant: *Matthew S. McCluskey, University of Vermont*

26.015. Enacting an Intergenerational Critical Participatory Epistemology via a Latinidad Upper Division Elective Course and Curriculum Resources. Division B - Curriculum Studies; Symposium

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 511C; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

isioning and Enacting a Latinidad Curriculum: A Framework

and Blueprint Grounded in Collaborative Inquiry. *Sophia Vazquez, Teachers College, Columbia University; Kathryn Caster, Teachers College, Columbia University; Limarys Caraballo, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Co-Creating with Youth: Developing and Implementing a Latinidad Conceptual Framework through YPAR and LatCrit. *Fabiola Quinones, Teachers College, Columbia University; Sophia Vazquez, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Enacting an Intergenerational Critical Participatory Epistemology via a Latinidad Upper Division Elective Course and Curriculum Resources. *Limarys Caraballo, Teachers College, Columbia University; Gisely Colon Lopez, City University of New York Graduate Center; Carolina Gomez, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Chairs: *Limarys Caraballo, Teachers College, Columbia University; Ezekiel J. Dixon-Roman, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Discussants: *Nolan L. Cabrera, University of Arizona; Amanda K. Earl, Teachers College, Columbia University*

26.016. It's in My Bones: Advancing the Embodiment of Theory for and by Blackgirls and Women. Division B - Curriculum Studies; Symposium

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304A; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Supporting Black Feminist Knowledge-Making in Science. *Natalie Annabelle Rae, Pennsylvania State University*

Beats of Endurance: A Womanist Spatial Examination of Black Women's Academic Refusal Through Hip Hop Testimonios. *Monet Harbison, Drexel University*

Theorizing 'Radical Openness' in Science Education: (Re)centering the Margins for Black Women Science Teachers. *Alexis Riley, New York University*

"Black women create... that's what we do": Intra-Black girlhood epistemologies as organic subversion. *Gabrielle Kubi, Boston College*

Speculative Liberation: Black Girls' Joy as Antifascist Pedagogy through Photovoice. *A Onuoha, Suffolk University*

Chair: *ReAnna S. Roby, University of Minnesota*

Discussant: *Tamara Butler, College of Charleston*

26.017. Teaching in the Ruins, Learning from the Land: Grounding Curriculum in Place and Possibility. Division B - Curriculum Studies; Paper Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 303B; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Ground and Grace to Grow On: Nurturing Nonviolent Education—and Curriculum Theorizing—via Narratives of the Forest School for Children in Cyprus. *Nicoletta Christodoulou, Frederick University; Molly Quinn, Louisiana State University*

Pacific Island Teachers' Perceptions of Place-Based Education in STEM. *Yu-Chieh Wu, University of Hawai'i at Mānoa; Jung Han, Purdue University; Pauline W.U. Chinn, University of Hawai'i at Manoa*

Teaching the Children of Our Ruin. *Clifford P. Harbour, University of North Texas*

The Land Speaks: A Borderland's Currence para Sanar La Herida. *Miguel Mendoza, University of Texas - Rio Grande Valley; Dalia Mendoza, University of Texas - Rio Grande Valley; Laura M. Jewett, University of Texas - Rio Grande Valley*

Trees as Embodying Local History/Knowledge/Wisdom: Unforgetting (Local) Histories and Imagining (Multispecies) Futures. *Asia S. Thomas, Augusta State University; Brandon Edwards-Schuth, Augusta University*

Chair: *Miguel Angel Garcia-Bocanegra, Northwestern University*
Discussant: *Hartley Banack, University of Northern British Columbia*

26.018. The Lab: Building Belonging and Motivation for Black Women in Higher Education. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Workshop

Westin Bonaventure, Level 2, Echo Park; 3:45-5:15pm

Chair: *Taylor Cummings, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*

Participants: *British Reynolds, University of Illinois at Chicago; Stacy Seward, University of Massachusetts - Lowell*

Presenters: *Kayla Hinkson-Grant, University of Florida; Kendra Seraphine, Wake Forest University; Jamela Joseph, Howard University*

26.019. Effect Estimation for Causality and Prediction: Multilevel and Single-case Designs, Machine Learning, and Distributional Assumptions. Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Paper Session
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, K-Town; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Defining and Estimating Causal Effects in Randomized Single-Case Alternating Treatment Design: A Counterfactual Approach. *Wen Luo, Texas A&M University; Chendong Li, Texas A&M University*

Effect Estimation in Randomized Single-Case Experimental Designs: The Influence of Undetected Extraneous Variables. *John M. Ferron, University of South Florida; Moses Muchiri Mohamed, University of South Florida; Joel R. Levin, University of Arizona; Tom Kratochwill*

Aligning One-stage and Two-stage Approaches for Combining Individual Participant and Aggregated Data in Meta-analysis. *Jingru Zhang, University of Wisconsin - Madison; James E. Pustejovsky, University of Wisconsin - Madison*
Item-Level Prediction of ADHD-Related Impairment Using Machine Learning and SEM Across Informants. *Xuefei Zou, University of Pennsylvania*

Jointly Optimal Design for Experiments Investigating Main and

Moderation Effects. *Zuchao Shen, University of Georgia; Benjamin Kelcey, University of Cincinnati; Zhenqiu Laura Lu, University of Georgia; Jingyang Li, University of Georgia; Jing Li, University of Georgia*

Chair: *Damian M. Berry, Baylor College of Medicine*

Discussant: *Graham Zulu, University of Denver*

26.020. Containment, Closures, and Desegregation in Twentieth and Twenty-First Century Schools. Division F - Historical Inquiry in Education; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 504; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

A History of Migrant Education in Southern Illinois 1960s-1990s. *Eileen Wertzberger, Kansas State University*

The Illusion of Integration: Segregated Schooling and Racial Containment in Richmond, California. *Christina Toma, University of California - Los Angeles*

Lessons from the Past: What Can the District of Columbia Public School Closures Tell Us About Current Educational Reform Debates? *Danielle M. Carrier, University of Southern Mississippi*

Teaching in a Polycrisis: Pedagogical Strategies of Black Educators During the Civil Rights Movement. *Tarsha I. Herelle, Johns Hopkins University; Andrene Castro, Virginia Commonwealth University; Phelton Cortez Moss, Virginia Commonwealth University; Tracy Booker, Virginia Commonwealth University; Kiari Cole, Virginia Commonwealth University*

How Grade Retention Became Naturalised within the Chilean Schools: A Documentary Analysis from 1925 to 2023. *Claudio Allende, Universidad de Chile; Verónica López, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Valparaíso; Machteld Vandecandelaere, University of Leuven*

Chair: *Deirdre Mayer Dougherty, Knox College*

Discussant: *Lori M. West, Knox College*

26.021. A.R.T. Official Intelligence: Critical Noise, Creative Tension, and How We Get Free. Division G - Social Context of Education; Demonstration/Performance
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 411 (Theatre); 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Verbs of Power: Spiritfood and Black Art in a Time of Tyranny. *Lasana D. Kazembe, Indiana University - Indianapolis*

Visual Counter-Narratives as Creative Resistance. *Luis Genaro Garcia, California State University - Sacramento*
Art as Healing: Interdisciplinary Pathways to Well-Being and Learning. *Yolanda Sealey-Ruiz, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Chairs: *Cleveland Hayes, Indiana University - Indianapolis; Arturo Anaya Servin, University of San Diego*

26.022. Racial and Gender Politics of Schooling. Division G - Social Context of Education; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304C;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Pedagogy as Gendered Practice: Hidden Curriculum of Gender in One U.S. High School Classrooms. *Kongji Qin, New York University*

Racializing and Historicizing Grade Levels. *Zachary A. Casey, Rhodes College; Shannon McManimon, Viterbo University*

The Curriculum of White Supremacy: Teaching, Learning, and the Racial Politics of Schooling. *Jungsoo Ahn, University of Michigan; Deborah Loewenberg Ball, University of Michigan*

The Draw-a-Woman Scientist Test: Exploring Schoolchildren's Perceptions of Women Scientists. *Laura Goldstein, University of Rhode Island; Sara Sweetman, University of Rhode Island*

Chair: *Linn E. Posey-Maddox, Temple University*

Discussant: *Omi Salas-SantaCruz, University of Utah*

26.023. Speaking Truth to Cacophony: Raciolinguistic Frameworks as Resistance to a Renewed Onslaught of Racist Policy. Division G - Social Context of Education; Symposium

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 309;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

From Sanctuary Promises to Praxis: Educator and Community Resistance to Raciolinguistic Profiling in Multilingual Spaces. *Jordan Gonzalez, St. John's University*

I Speak, I Write, I Resist: A Long-term English Learner's Counterstory of Defiance. *Hosna Jabalameli, Unaffiliated; Yalda M. Kaveh, Arizona State University*

Enshrining English, Censoring Equity: Language Appropriation in Anti-Diversity Mandates. *Chris K. Chang-Bacon, University of Virginia; Kara Mitchell Viesca, University of Nebraska - Lincoln*

Chair: *Diana Lalata, University of Pennsylvania*

Discussants: *Aris M. Clemons, University of Tennessee; Maria Cioe-Pena, University of Pennsylvania; Manka M. Varghese, University of Washington; Kate Seltzer, Rowan University*

26.024. Teaching Under Surveillance: Censorship, Book Bans, and the Struggle for Educational Freedom. Division G - Social Context of Education; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 301B;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Censoring Educator Preparation: Paving the Pathway to Educational Authoritarianism? *Dilys Schoorman, Florida Atlantic University*

Shelf Control: Dissecting Discourses on Book Bans. *Jin Lee,*

University of Louisiana at Lafayette; Olivia Peltier, University of Louisiana at Lafayette

The Historical Pattern of Black Erasure: How Whiteness Operates as Property in State Education Policy. *Logan Johnson, The Integrity Line; Amy N. Farley, University of Cincinnati*

"You Better Not Make the News": Exploring English Teachers' Experiences with Censorship and Book Banning. *Emily Freeman, University of Wisconsin - Eau Claire; Logan Ackerman, University of Wisconsin - Eau Claire; Scout Feldman, University of Wisconsin - Eau Claire; Alyssa Greenwood, University of Wisconsin - Eau Claire*

Chair: *Rachelle S. Savitz, East Carolina University*

Discussant: *James Wright, Temple University*

26.025. When Numbers Feel White: Emotionality, Microaggressions, and Identity in Math Education.

Division G - Social Context of Education; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 409AB;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

White Feelings, Black and Brown Fatigue: The Emotional Weight of Mathematical Legitimacy. *Jennifer A. Chabriel-Amara, University of San Diego; Nallely Gecik, University of San Diego; Cheryl E. Matias, University of San Diego*

Black Students' Perceptions of Mathematics Teacher Treatment on their Mathematics Motivation. *Charlotte A. Agger, Indiana University; Korinthia D. Nicolai, Indiana University; Monica L. Miles, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Whitney N. McCoy, Duke University; Terrell R Morton, University of Illinois at Chicago*

Whiteness, Emotionality, and Novice Teachers' Commitments to Anti-Racist Mathematics Teaching. *Craig J. Willey, Indiana University - Indianapolis*

"There Are a Lot of Ignorant Students": Girls of Color Perspectives About Discussing Controversial Issues in Mathematics Class. *Kari Kokka, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*

Chair: *Cheryl E. Matias, University of San Diego*

Discussant: *Danny Bernard Martin, University of Illinois at Chicago*

26.026. Belonging and Becoming: Racial Affinity Group Caucus Pedagogy in Medical Education. Division I -

Education in the Professions; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 501C;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Reimagining Professional Identity Formation Through Racial Affinity Group Caucusing in Medical Education. *Leanna Lewis, University of California - Berkeley; Diana Ponce, University of California - San Francisco*

Building Faculty, Staff, and Learner Community Through Racial Caucusing in Family Medicine. *Monica Hahn,*

University of California - San Francisco; Sharon Washington, Sharon Washington Consulting; Manuel Tapia, University of California - San Francisco; Diana Coffa, University of California - San Francisco

Belonging in Practice: Racial Affinity Group Caucusing and Professional Identity Formation in Pediatric Residency. *Jyothi Marbin, University of California – San Francisco; Leanna Lewis, University of California - Berkeley; Camila Cribb Fabersunne, University of California; Camila DePierola, University of California - San Francisco; Faheemah N. Mustafaa, University of California - Davis*

Panel Discussion: Emergent Themes and Future Directions. *Leanna Lewis, University of California - Berkeley; Jyothi Marbin, University of California – San Francisco; Monica Hahn, University of California - San Francisco; Camila Cribb Fabersunne, University of California*

Chair: *D'Anne Duncan, University of California - San Francisco*
Discussant: *Leanna Lewis, University of California - Berkeley*

26.027. Developing Culturally Responsive Curriculum in Higher Education in Challenging Times. Division J -

Postsecondary Education; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum H; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Centering Latine/Hispanic, Native American, and Indigenous Students' Ways of Knowing in Curriculum and Pedagogy. *Lauren R. Contreras, Northern Arizona University; Renee White Eyes, Northern Arizona University; Susana H. Hernandez, Northern Arizona University; Alana Aiko Uilani Kennedy, Northern Arizona University; Cynthia D. Villarreal, Northern Arizona University*

Teaching and Learning for Wholeness and Wellness in Higher Education. *Maryann Krikorian, Loyola Marymount University*

Validating Student Identities Through Culturally Responsive Curriculum. *V Simone May, Florida State University; Sarah Fucillo, Lindsey Wilson College; Patrick Murphy, Lindsey Wilson College*

Decolonizing the Curriculum in the Age of Digital Structural Violence. *Laura Harrison, Ohio University; Samba Bah, Ohio University*

Chair: *Lauren R. Contreras, Northern Arizona University*
Discussants: *Rick Rantz, Allan Hancock College; LeeAnne McNulty, Allan Hancock College*

26.028. Student Learning and Engagement in Community Colleges and Beyond. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum F; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Cultivating Civic Character in College: Virtue, Vocation, and the Moral Purpose of Postsecondary Learning. *David J.*

Roof, Ball State University

Evaluating the Impact of an Innovative Statistics Corequisite Course on Community College Student Math Outcomes. *Kirk Walters, WestEd; Chun-Wei Kevin Huang, WestEd; Karon Klipple, Carnegie Foundation for the Advancement of Teaching; Kathleen D'Silva, WestEd; Min Huang, WestEd; Danielle Raymond, Université de Sherbrooke*

Exploring the Roles of Racism and Campus Responses in Student Belonging and Resource Use at Community Colleges. *Carlton J. Fong, Texas State University; Pedram Zarei, Texas State University; Semilore F. Adelugba, Texas State University; Agustín J. García, Texas A&M University–Corpus Christi*

Imagining Futures: Learning Assistantships as an Avenue to Support Community College Student Development. *Paula Jakopovic, University of Nebraska - Omaha; Brigid Howard, Metropolitan Community College; Naomi Mardock, Metropolitan Community College*

Chair: *La Quirshia Fennell, Claremont Graduate University*
Discussant: *Regina J. Deil-Amen, University of Arizona*

26.029. The Possibilities of "Green Book" Approach to Higher Education. Division J - Postsecondary Education;

Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum G; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

The Green Book as Change: Ethnographic Reflections on a Black Undergraduate Mentoring Course. *Michael W. Moses, University of California - Riverside; Briana Savage, University of California - Riverside*

Governing Boards as Architects For Black Campus Success: A Green Book to Establishing a Governance Blueprint. *Raquel M. Rall, University of California - Riverside*

Navigating the Philanthropy Landscape: A Green Book Guide for Charitable Giving in Higher Education. *Everrett A. Smith, University of Cincinnati*

The Souls of Black College Students: Reclaiming Space and Community in the Digital Age. *Tré Watkins, University of San Diego; Heather Streets, University of San Francisco*

Guarding the Black Body and Mind When Traveling Through Higher Education. *Tiffany Green, American University*

Chair: *Juana Hollingsworth, Morgan State University*
Discussant: *Antar A. Tichavakunda, University of California - Santa Barbara*

26.030. Multilingual Realities: Translanguaging in Schools.

Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 7; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Exploring Elementary Teachers' Experiences in Enacting Translanguaging Practices with Migrant and Refugee

Students. *Katya Koubek, James Madison University; Stephanie A. Wasta, James Madison University*

From Uncertainty to Advocacy: A Longitudinal Study of a Teacher's Journey in Translanguaging Pedagogy. *ChiuYin Cathy Wong, Monmouth University; Mariella Gallagher, Monmouth University*

Heritage Language Maintenance and Loss: Teacher Candidates' Personal Experiences and Perspectives. *Christy Y. Lao, San Francisco State University*

Translanguaging in Action: A Single Case Study of Pedagogical Acts in a Newcomer Classroom. *Jinhua Wang, Kansas State University; Socorro Herrera, Kansas State University; Kendra Herrera, Kansas State University*

Developing Critical Multilingual Language Awareness in Teacher Education: Student Teachers' Reflections on Theory and Practice. *Amanda Susan Byrd, University of Texas at Austin; Angela Maria Tuason Villamizar, University of Texas at Austin*

Chair: *Eman Abo-Zaed Arar, Texas State University*

Discussant: *Karina Guerrero, Claremont Graduate University*

26.031. Refusals of Erasure: Centering Indigenous Resurgence as Survivance in Teacher Education. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum J; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Refusals of Erasure: Centering Indigenous Resurgence as Survivance. *Leilani Sabzalian, University of Oregon*

Centering Indigenous Resurgence as Survivance in Teacher Education. *Valerie J. Shirley, University of Arizona*

Centering Indigenous Resurgence as Survivance in TE. *Frank Deer, University of Manitoba; Hugh Burnam, Roswell Park Comprehensive Cancer Center*

Refusals of Erasure: Centering Indigenous Resurgence as Survivance in TE. *Bryan McKinley Jones Brayboy, Northwestern University*

Refusals of Erasure. *Jarita Greyeyes, McMaster University*

Chair: *Jennifer Brant, University of Toronto - OISE*

Discussant: *Jeremy Garcia, University of Arizona*

26.032. Reimagining Teacher Education: Equity, Technology, and Globalization in Preservice Preparation. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 8; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Culturally Responsive Literacy Boards: Examining a Tool for Literacy Teacher Preparation. *Doris Villarreal, Ohio University; Yvette M. Regalado, University of Texas - San Antonio; Samuel DeJulio, University of Texas - San Antonio*

Forging Connections through Linguistic and Cultural Practices: Asian American Student Teachers Leveraging Identity and Experience. *Kathryn Struthers Ahmed, Hunter College -*

CUNY; Sonia Begum, Hunter College; Jia Yan Jiang, Hunter College - CUNY; Oumwatie Sookkall, Hunter College - CUNY; Jessie Song, Hunter College - CUNY; Victoria Song, Hunter College - CUNY; Samantha Wong, Hunter College - CUNY

Preparing Pre-Service Teachers for Multilingual Classrooms through Practical Wisdom. *Han Zheng, University of Florida; Mark B. Pacheco, University of Florida; Jared McKee, University of Florida; Yi Lai, University of Florida; Bektı Febriarti, University of Florida*

Chair: *Kyle Elizabeth Miller, Illinois State University*

26.033. Tending Our Field's Garden: Research Deans' (re)Imagining the Future of Teaching and Teacher Education. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 6; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Tending Our Field's Garden: A San Diego Dean (re)Imagining the Future of Teaching and Teacher Education. *Kimberly A. White-Smith, University of San Diego*

Tending Our Field's Garden: A California Dean (re)Imagining the Future of Teaching and Teacher Education. *Roxanne Greitz Miller, Chapman University*

Tending Our Field's Garden: A Philadelphia Dean (re)Imagining the Future of Teaching and Teacher Education. *Monika Williams Shealey, Temple University*

Tending Our Field's Garden: A Texas Dean (re)Imagining the Future of Teaching and Teacher Education. *Frank Hernandez, Texas Christian University*

Chairs: *Erica D. McCray, University of Florida; Nicol R. Howard, Chapman University*

Discussant: *Ebony Terrell Shockley, University of Maryland*

26.034. Data, AI, and Power: Critical Perspectives on Equity and Influence in Education. Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 10; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Data Rot is a Central Issue of Publicly Accessible Open State School Education Indicator Datasets. *Alex J. Bowers, Teachers College, Columbia University; Ghipsel Cibrian, Teachers College, Columbia University; Maeghan Sill, Teachers College, Columbia University; Yeonsoo Choi, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Echoes of Empire: Generative AI, Colonial Radio, and the Global North's Influence on Curriculum and Data in Education. *Yi Wu, Pennsylvania State University*

Echoes of Urgency: Comparing Calls for AI Literacy, Financial Literacy, and Digital Literacy. *Alexander M. Hoffman, AleDev Research*

How States Conceptualize AI and Equity in Education: A

Policy Analysis of Emerging K–12 Guidance. *Vincent Cho, Boston College; Sergio David Barragán, Boston College; Alex J. Bowers, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Reimagining AI Policy in Higher Education: Insights from Faculty and Policymakers. *Dini Noor Arini, Washington State University*

Chair: *Adejah Taylor, University of California - Los Angeles*

Discussant: *Bo Pei, University of South Florida*

26.035. Unforgetting Professional Ethics: Educators Resisting Policy Mandates Misaligned with Justice. Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 1; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Between Mandate and Method: Teachers' Sensemaking with Science of Reading Rollout. *Wanda Roshell DeBrewer, Morgan State University; Astrid Mariel Sierra Mejia, University of Maryland; Jessica B Crawford, University of Maryland; Nemain Morgan Curtis, George Washington University; Donald J. Bolger, University of Maryland; Simone Gibson, Morgan State University; Margaret Polizos Peterson, University of Maryland*

Enacting Prevention, Negotiating Power: Prevention Staff as Critical Agents of Title IX Policy. *Elizabeth Lopez, Claremont Graduate University*

Navigating Accountability in Writing Teacher Preparation: Teacher Educators' Response to Restrictive Literacy Policy. *Kristen Driscoll, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Teacher Resistance, Compliance, and Resistant Compliance with Laws Mandating the Outing of Transgender Students. *Xavier Fields, University of Michigan*

Understanding the Influence of State Regulations on School Librarians' Collection Development Practices. *Jenna Spiering, University of South Carolina; Valerie Byrd Fort, University of South Carolina - Columbia; Jennifer Moore, University of South Carolina*

Chair: *Darrius A. Stanley, University of Minnesota*

Discussant: *Miyoshi Juergensen, University of Alabama - Birmingham*

SIG Sessions

26.036. Reforming the Math Hierarchy: Policy, Practice, and the Politics of Equity in Access and Pathways. SIG-Access, Detracking, and Tracking; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 9; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

A Critical Policy Analysis of Statewide Public Comment on Math Pathways Programs. *Margaret Thornton, Rowan University; Sonji F. Walker, San Francisco State University;*

Jamela Joseph, Howard University; Yanni Akinne, University of Virginia

A Latent Class Analysis of High School Student Advanced Mathematics Coursework and Depressive Symptoms.

Kristian Edosomwan, University of Houston; Collin Perryman, Arizona State University

Breaking or Building Tracks? Community College

Mathematics Access and Calculus Success. *Mike Bostick, Central Wyoming College; Miriam M. Sanders, University of Wyoming; Mark A. Perkins, University of Colorado - Colorado Springs; Scott Chamberlin, University of Wyoming*

From Policy to Practice: Challenges and Effects of the Grade 9 De-streamed Math Curriculum Implementation in Ontario, Canada. *Zian Zhang, University of Toronto - OISE; Douglas E. McDougall, University of Toronto - OISE*

Tracking and Placement Politics in North Carolina: Pushback, Progress, and Policy Reform. *Constance Clark, Rutgers University - Newark*

Chair: *Constance Clark, Rutgers University - Newark*

Discussant: *Elizabeth Huffaker, University of Florida*

26.037. Adult Community, Literacy, and Language Educators: Professional Development and Perspectives. SIG-Adult Literacy and Adult Education; Paper Session

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, La Brea; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Adult Education ESL Students and Instructors in the United States: A Systematic Literature Review. *Benjamin M. James, University of Delaware; Kylie A. Kenner, University of California - Santa Cruz; George C. Bunch, University of California - Santa Cruz; Amy E. Brown, Teachers College, Columbia University; Julia Raufman, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Critical Thinking in Adult Literacy Education: Examining the Perceptions and Practices of Adult Educators. *Hilal Ayan, Florida State University*

Design cases and professional development programs for educators in crisis. *Faridah Pawan, Indiana University*

Promoting Experiential Learning and Research Skills Among Community Educators: Service-Learning and Photovoice as Professional Development. *Clarena Larrotta, Texas State University; Fasih Raza, Texas State University*

Serving adults with difficulty reading in Indiana: A stakeholders' needs assessment. *Amy Pickard, Indiana University; Lara Pastore, Indiana Department of Workforce Development*

Chair: *Emily Dobrich, University of Toronto - OISE*

Discussant: *Vanessa Hammler Kenon, University of Texas - San Antonio*

26.038. Instructional Practices for Multilingual Learners with Disabilities. SIG-Bilingual Education Research; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 501B; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

The Promise of Bilingual Drama-based Instruction for Young Bilingual Children with Disabilities: A Case Study. *Katie Bernstein, Arizona State University; Theresa Moen, Arizona State University; Lauren van Huisstede, Arizona State University; Melissa Pierce-Rivera, Midwestern University*

Learning to Teach Inclusively in Bilingual Education: A “Toma-y-Daca” Dance for Permeable Bilingual Spaces. *Patricia Martínez-Álvarez, Teachers College, Columbia University; Belinda Arana, Teachers College, Columbia University; Kitty Conlon Macias, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Parents Choosing Dual Language for Children with Disabilities: “Se Le Abrió Su Mundo Otra Vez”. *Carly C. Leech, The University of Texas at San Antonio; Jorge L. Solis, University of Texas - San Antonio*

Chairs: *Sunaina Shenoy, University of New Mexico; Rosalia Pacheco, University of New Mexico; Sara E.N. Kangas, Lehigh University*

Discussant: *Trish Morita-Mullaney, Purdue University*

26.039. Teacher Practices and Professional Development with AI. SIG-Computer and Internet Application in Education; Paper Session

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, San Gabriel A; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Exploring computing attitude profiles and teacher instructional practices with elementary school students following teacher PD. *Santiago Ospina-Tabares, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Nitasha Mathayas, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Shehneela Naz, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Chrystalla Mouza, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Hilary Mead, University of Delaware*

Elementary Pre-Service Teachers’ Experiences Using ChatGPT to Generate Early Literacy Materials. *Kristen H. Gregory, East Carolina University; Christiana K. Kfoury, East Carolina University*

Exploring the Emotion-Coping-Outcome Dynamics among Pre-Service Teachers in Generative AI-Assisted Teaching. *Yangyang Guo, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Chan Wang, The Education University of Hong Kong; Hongbiao Yin, The Chinese University of Hong Kong*

From Human to Augmented Intelligence: Using Generative AI in Planning for Teaching among K-12 Teachers. *Okan Arslan, University of West Georgia; Li Cao, University of West Georgia*

What Teachers Discuss and How They Perceive and Feel: Topic Modeling and Sentiment Analysis of a Generative Artificial Intelligence Learning Group on Facebook. *Zicong Song, The University of Hong Kong; Chun Lai, The University of Hong Kong; Xianhan Huang, The Education University of Hong Kong; Chin-Hsi Lin, University of Hong*

Kong; Zhong Sun, Capital Normal University

Chair: *Chin-Hsi Lin, University of Hong Kong*

Discussant: *Xianhan Huang, The Education University of Hong Kong*

26.040. Pakikipag-Kapwa: Filipino Indigenous Ways of Knowing for Decolonial Studies in Filipino-American Educational Research. SIG-Decolonial, Postcolonial, and Anti-Colonial Studies in Education; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 301A; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Kapwa as a Decolonial Lens in Culturally Sustaining Pedagogy. *Eric Claravall, California State University - Sacramento*
Tsismis as Decolonizing Epistemology. *Elizabeth Isidro, Western Michigan University*

Kapwa, Kuwento, Kalaro: Engaging Filipino Children in Literary and Mediated Spaces. *Cheeno Marlo Sayuno, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Kapwa as a Speculative Lens for Interrogating Sociotechnical Systems and Tech. *Francisco Castro, New York University*

Chair: *Eric Claravall, California State University - Sacramento*

Discussant: *Roland Sintos Coloma, Wayne State University*

26.041. Democracy Needs Education: Civic Learning Across Global Contexts in Troubling Times. SIG-Democratic Citizenship in Education; Symposium

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 2; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

A Decolonial Analysis of Curriculum Intentions for Global Citizenship Education in two Asian Societies. *Theresa Alviar Martin, Kennesaw State University; Mark C. Baildon, Indiana University*

Segregated Civics: Documenting and Disrupting Segregated Educational Experiences and Political Understandings in a ‘Red’ State”. *dinorah sanchez loza, The Ohio State University*

Nurturing Democracy from the Ground Up: Civic Education in Türkiye Amidst Democratic Backsliding. *Betul Demiray Sandiraz, Michigan State University; Anne-Lise F. Halvorsen, Michigan State University*

Chair: *Erin A. Bronstein, University of Michigan - Dearborn*

Discussant: *Aviv Cohen, Hebrew University of Jerusalem*

26.042. Inclusion or Illusion? Student-Informed Reflexive Practices in K-12 Settings. SIG-Disability Studies in Education; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 511AB; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Deconstructing Not to Build. *Kristen Luppino Witzling, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Resisting Right & Wrong — Humanizing Disabled Students

through Student Work Analysis in Mathematics Teacher Learning. *Mikaela Zetley, University of California - Los Angeles; Jennifer Schexnayder, University of California - Los Angeles; Megan L. Franke, University of California - Los Angeles*

The In/dependence Curricular Quandary for Students with Intellectual Disabilities. *Jessica K. Bacon, Montclair State University*

The Lived Experiences of Disabled Students in Inclusive Classrooms. *Tanner Mizel, University of San Diego*

Chair: *Chelsea Tracy-Bronson, Stockton University*

Discussant: *Tamara Handy, Teachers College, Columbia University*

26.043. Beyond Degrees: Making Space and Policies for Generational Knowledge in the Early Childhood Care and Education Workforce. SIG-Early Education and Child Development; Symposium

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Georgia I; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

“Learning at the Knee”: Intergenerational Practitioner Knowledge of Black Girls in ECE. *Morgan Faison, University of Georgia; Stacie Abdallah, University of Georgia*

Generations of Care: Unlisted Home-Based Care Givers Describe the Policies They Need. *Zoelene Hill, New York Academy of Medicine*

Beyond Certification: Uplifting Hispanic Caregivers in Fragmented Early Childhood Systems. *Maria Mavrides Calderon, Hunter College - CUNY*

Black Matriarchal Pedagogy: Reimagining Teacher Education Through a Radical Ethos of Care. *Crystasany R. Turner, University of Wisconsin - Milwaukee*

Chair: *Zoelene Hill, New York Academy of Medicine*

Discussant: *Porsche Boddicker, Howard University*

26.044. Reconstructing School-Family Partnerships in Urban Schools through Culturally Sustaining Leadership. SIG-Educational Change; Symposium

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum B; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Reconstructing School-Family Partnerships in Urban Schools through Culturally Sustaining Leadership. *LeAnne C. Salazar Montoya, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Emily Victoria Garcia, University of Nevada Las Vegas; Carmen Beck, California State University - San Bernardino; Tracie Trinidad, Aurora Public Schools; Kristin L. Kew, New Mexico State University; Griselda Galindo-Vargas, Texas State University; Juanita Galaviz, Texas State University; Gina Delgado, UnidoUS; Pinyi Wang, University of Florida*

Writing for and with Families: Centering Parental Voice in Urban Education Research. *Gina Delgado, UnidoUS;*

Carmen Beck, California State University - San Bernardino; LeAnne C. Salazar Montoya, University of Nevada - Las Vegas

Activism in Urban Schooling. *Tracie Trinidad, Aurora Public Schools; Griselda Galindo-Vargas, Texas State University; Sharon Ross, East Texas A&M University*

Chair: *LeAnne C. Salazar Montoya, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*

Discussant: *Emily Victoria Garcia, University of Nevada Las Vegas*

26.045. Place-based and participatory learning. SIG-

Environmental Education; Paper Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 506; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Beyond the Classroom Walls: National Patterns, Barriers, and Benefits of Outdoor Learning in U.S. Schools. *Luke Parker, Australian Catholic University*

BioBlitzing as an Experiential Learning Tool for High School Students and its Learning Outcomes. *Jennifer Gribben, University of Southern California; Gale M. Sinatra, University of Southern California*

Learning Amid Drought: Socio-Educational Responses to Environmental Crisis in Rural Chilean Schools. *Juan de Dios Oyarzun, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Valparaíso*

Reinterpreting Photovoice: Exploring young children’s Environmental Concerns in India. *Sylvia Christine Almeida, Monash University; Tamralipta Patra, Monash University*

Play, Learn, Empower: a Design Model of Student Engagement in Environmental Education. *Julia DeVoy, Boston College*

Chair: *YIJING LYU, Nanjing Normal University*

Discussant: *Elizabeth Shores, Rowan University*

26.046. Reforming Pedagogies and Creating Powerful Knowledge in Singapore: Examining System Rebuilding over Two Decades. SIG-International Studies; Symposium

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304B; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

The Epistemic Work of Teachers: Trajectories of Powerful Knowledge and Pedagogical Changes in Singapore. *Dennis Kwek, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University*

The Interactional Work of Teachers: Dialogues for Powerful Knowledge in Singapore. *Hock Huan Goh, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University*

The Assessment Work of Teachers: Assessing and Accessing Forms of Powerful Knowledge. *Hwei Ming Wong, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University*

Achievement Goal Profiles and Motivational Dynamics in Singapore’s Evolving Educational Landscape. *Qianqian Pan, Nanyang Technological University*

Chair: *Dennis Kwek, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University*

Discussant: *Donald J. Peurach, University of Michigan*

26.047. Critical & Equity-Oriented Leadership Preparation.

SIG-Learning and Teaching in Educational Leadership;
Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, La Cienega; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

A Review of the Literature: Educational Leaders Imagining Futures of Cultural Proficiency. *Brooke Soles, California State University - San Marcos; Theresa A. Meyerott, California State University - Los Angeles; Jaime E. Welborn, Saint Louis University; Peter Flores, Praxis Lead Equity, LLC*

Educational Design for Collective Liberation: Rethinking Leadership Development in a Critical EdD Program. *Violet Ballard, San Francisco State University; Barbara A. Henderson, San Francisco State University; Chu Hsi Tseng, San Francisco State University; Robert Gabriner, San Francisco State University*

Trauma-Informed and Culturally-Responsive School Leadership for African American Male Students with Emotional Disabilities. *Charisse Bynoe, Teachers College, Columbia University*

What Are Students Learning in an Equity-centered Educational Leadership Program? *Carla Finkelstein, Towson University*

Chair: *Kimberly Jamison, University of North Carolina - Wilmington*

26.048. Data Science Education: Re-Envisioning for 21st Century Teaching, Learning, and Research. SIG-

Learning Sciences; Structured Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 515B;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

1. Expanding and Enriching K-12 Computational Thinking Pathways with Data Science Competencies (Poster 1). *Shuchi Grover, Looking Glass Ventures; Quinn Burke, Digital Promise; Sharin R. Jacob, Digital Promise Global*
2. Teaching the Past to Build Equitable AI Futures with Emancipatory Artificial Intelligence (Poster 2). *Thema Monroe-White, George Mason University*
3. Data Science: A Pathway for Integration Across K-12 Disciplines (Poster 3). *Kathi Fidler, Brown University*
4. Developing Data Arguments: The Case of a Professional Learning Community of Secondary Mathematics Teachers (Poster 4). *Travis Weiland, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Caitlin Ireland, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Laura Shelton, University of Houston; Mandana Delavari, University of Houston*
5. How Elementary Teachers Design and Implement Inclusive and Interest-Based Data Science Units (Poster 5). *Danielle*

C. Herro, Clemson University; Golnaz Arastoopour Irgens, Vanderbilt University

6. Getting Local with Data: Possibilities and Pitfalls Across Three US Place-based Data Science Research Projects (Poster 6). *Leah Rosenbaum, Teachers College, Columbia University; Kathryn Lanouette, William & Mary; Cody C. Pritchard, University of Tennessee; Bradley Russell Holtz, University of Tennessee*
 7. Data Science in K-12 Social Studies: Censoring Teacher Voice (Poster 7). *Hyein Jee, Michigan State University; Anne Drew Hu, Michigan State University; Aman Yadav, Michigan State University*
 8. Finding the Sweet Spot in Interdisciplinary Data Science Education: The Data Puzzles Model (Poster 8). *Kerri Wingert, Good Question Research & Evaluation; Jonathan Griffith, Cooperative Institute for Research in Environmental Sciences; Joshua Rosenberg, University of Tennessee; Christine Okochi, University of Colorado - Boulder; Kristin Hunter-Thomson, Dataspire Education & Evaluation LLC; Kimberly Jones, University of Tennessee; Karla Citlali Lemus Gordillo, University of Colorado - Boulder; Annette Brickley, Dataspire Education & Evaluation, LLC; Anne Gold, University of Colorado - Boulder; Alyse Thurber, University of Colorado - Boulder*
- Chairs: *Justice Toshiba Walker, University of Maryland; Joshua Rosenberg, University of Tennessee; Colby Tofel-Greth, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Discussant: *Stephanie D. Teasley, University of Michigan*

26.049. Teaching Practices and the Learning Sciences. SIG-Learning Sciences; Paper Session

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Beaudry A; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

- Characterizing preservice teachers' in-the-moment interpretations of student resources: Leveraging AI-supported virtual reality. *Nuodi Zhang, Florida State University; Fengfeng Ke, University of Maryland; Chih-Pu Dai, Texas A&M University*
- Did the Computer Get It Right? Students Analyzing and Challenging Data Visualizations in ELA Class. *Victor R. Lee, Stanford University; Nichole Nomura, University of Wyoming; Daniela Gamboa Zapatel, Stanford University; Georgii Korotkov, Stanford University; Sarah Levine, Stanford University*
- Evaluating AI's interpretations of Teachers' Mathematical Thinking. *Kun Wang, Rethink Learning Labs; Rachael Eriksen Brown, Pennsylvania State University - Abington; Chandra H. Orrill, Rethink Learning Labs; Cheng Tang, University of Georgia; Shiyu Wang, University of Georgia; Yaxuan Yang, University of Georgia; Allan S. Cohen, University of Georgia*
- External Factors Predicting the Perceived Usefulness of an Online Teacher Professional Learning Platform. *Amos Jeng, University of Michigan; HaeJin Lee, University of Illinois at*

Urbana-Champaign; Hana Kearfott, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Sarah Burns, University of Chicago; Cheryl Moran, University of Chicago; George Vythoulkas, University of Chicago; Joseph R. Cimpian, New York University; Meg Bates, University of Illinois System; Nigel Bosch, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Michelle Perry, University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign

Positioning AI as an Active Collaborator in Sensemaking with AI-Generated Feedback. *Seth Van Doren, University of California - Irvine; Jacqueline Nguyen, University of California - Irvine; Lily Wu, University of California - Irvine; Abril Gomez, University of California Irvine; June Ahn, University of California - Irvine*

Chair: *Soobin Jeon, University of Michigan*

26.050. Motivation in Education SIG In-Progress Research

Event. SIG-Motivation in Education; Invited Speaker Session

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Beaudry B; 3:45-5:15pm

Chairs: *Sanheeta Shankar, McGill University; Wonjoon Cha, The Ohio State University*

Participants: *Rebecca Brown, Wayne State University; Samantha Mackie, University of Ottawa; RoseMarie Rohrs, Boston College; Alison C. Koenka, University of Oklahoma; Miranda G. Goldstein, University of California - Irvine; Yining Yan, Columbia University; Eric Asare, Old Dominion University; Ella Marie White, University of Oklahoma; Qingqing Zhou, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Joseph Burey, University of Minnesota; Carlton J. Fong, Texas State University; Yucheng Bao, Vanderbilt University; Halle Jacobs, Teachers College, Columbia University; Anushree Bhatia, University of Michigan; Kennedy Ryan Webster, University of Oklahoma; Maisha Farzana Mumu, University of Oklahoma; Kanvarbir Gill, University of Oklahoma; Candace Andrews, University of Oklahoma; Michael Abdul Ghani Berro, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Quynh P. Nguyen, University of Oklahoma; Swetha Siripurapu, University of Oklahoma; Jessica Newhouse, University of Oklahoma; Maryamsadat Mirpour, Texas State University; Aarushi Gupta, Purdue University; Emmaus Patterson, Purdue University; Sanheeta Shankar, McGill University; Jessica Hunter, McGill University; Sydney Perkins, McGill University; Kyla Leong-Poi, Ottawa University; Kristy A. Robinson, McGill University; Ranellucci John, University of Ottawa*

26.051. A Collective of Diverse Narrative Explorations: A Generative Space for Sharing Approaches to Storying, Identity, Equity, and Inquiry. SIG-Narrative Research; Structured Poster Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 515A; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

1. Collecting, Analyzing, and Reporting Storied Data:

Articulating Multiple Narrative Research Approaches for Greater Methodological Transparency (Poster 1). *Carlo Cinaglia, Florida State University*

2. Living Digiphrenia: A Scholarly Personal Narrative on Fractured Identity and Academic Care (Poster 2). *Suzanne L. Porath, Kansas State University*
3. The Narrative Imperative: Foundational Principles for Preserving Human Agency in Generative AI-Assisted Learning (Poster 3). *Sheng-Ya Juan, National Yang Ming Chiao Tung University; Hsiao-feng Tsai, National Academy for Educational Research - Taiwan; Ken-Zen Chen, National Yang Ming Chiao Tung University*
4. Resisting Deficit Discourses: A Narrative Inquiry into the Mathematics Learning Experiences of African American Community College Students (Poster 4). *Antoinette Brooks, Morgan State University*
5. Becoming a Narrative Inquiry Student (Poster 5). *Mopelola Folashade Oyeniran, University of Alabama*
6. The Tale of Three Elephants: An Autobiography Through the Lens of an Asian American Educator (Poster 6). *Nipah Onkananuwonk, Texas A&M University*
7. Not Movers, Not Leavers: Rebuilding the Teaching Profession Amid Changing Educational Landscapes (Poster 7). *Cammie Justus-Smith, Virginia Commonwealth University; Georgia Heyward, Virginia Commonwealth University*

Chair: *William J. Davis, Southern Utah University*

26.052. Organizing for Equity and Inclusion: Innovative Theorizing Across the P-20 Educational Ecosystem. SIG-Organizational Theory; Paper Session

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Santa Barbara C; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

From Resistance to Reimagination: African-Centered School Leadership and the Organizational Core. *Bodunrin O. Banwo, University of Massachusetts - Boston*

Disrupting or Reproducing Racialized Hiring? Assessing Faculty Cluster Hiring's Racial Equity Potential Across Disciplinary Contexts. *Baili Park, University of Pittsburgh; Charlie Díaz, University of Pittsburgh; Román Liera, Montclair State University; Aireale J. Rodgers, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Heather N. McCambly, University of Pittsburgh*

Organizational conditions as mediators of equity-focused family engagement. *Jennifer Gaul, University of Washington*

"I heard they put a litter box in the bathroom": Teacher Sensemaking around Restrictive Education Policies. *Tabitha Bonilla, Northwestern University; Jennifer R. Cowhy, University of Arkansas*

Organizing for Coherence: How State Structures Enable or Constrain Collaboration Between General and Special Education. *Tye Austin Ripma, Stanford University*

Discussant: *Jeff Walls, University of Iowa*

26.053. Complicated and Complicating Questions About the Role of AI in Qualitative Inquiry. SIG-Qualitative Research; Symposium
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Echo Park; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

The Methodological Footprint of Generative AI. *Jessica Nina Lester, Indiana University; Jessica Van Cleave, Gardner-Webb University; Mirka E. Koro, Arizona State University*

Walking with Colossus: An Inconvenient Ethics with AI in Qualitative Inquiry. *Susan N. Nordstrom, University of Alabama*

“We Are All Chimeras”: A Queer Cyborg Manifesto on Artificial Intelligence in Qualitative Research. *Stephanie Anne Shelton, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*

AI and Interviews: The Pursuit of Meaning. *Kathryn J. Roulston, University of Georgia; Hannah Ameli, University of Georgia; Younghyun Kim, University of Georgia*

What do humans have to do with qualitative research ,and what can human researchers offer to qualitative research that AI cannot? *Johanna Creswell Báez, University of Colorado - Colorado Springs*

Chairs: *Jessica Nina Lester, Indiana University; Jessica Van Cleave, Gardner-Webb University; Mirka E. Koro, Arizona State University*

Discussant: *David L. Carlson, Arizona State University*

26.054. Education amid an Era of Rising White Christian Nationalism and Political Extremism. SIG-Religion and Education; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 303A; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Who Are “Our Children”? White Christian Nationalist Rhetoric in West Michigan School Board Campaigns. *Joel E. Berends, Michigan State University; Katherine M. Ward, Michigan State University; Kasun Gajasinghe, Michigan State University; Mary M. Juzwik, Michigan State University; Rebecca L. Witte, Michigan State University*

Secular Apologetics: Mindfulness in K-12 Public Schools and Appeasing White Christian Nationalism. *Funie Hsu/Chhi, San Jose State University*

Faith and Justice for Whom? A Critical Discourse Analysis of LGBTQ+ Topics in Catholic Schools. *Jonathon E. Sawyer, University of Colorado - Boulder*

Between Absence and Stereotype: Judaism in PK-12 History Standards. *Anna Yonas, University of Kansas; Colleen Fitzpatrick, University of Toledo; Amy E. Allen, Virginia Tech*

Secular Policy, Religious Diversity: Lessons from Singapore for Global Citizenship Education (GCE). *Christian A. Hansen, Virginia Tech*

Chair: *Kevin J. Burke, University of Georgia*

26.055. What Does it Take to Maximize HQIM's Potential to Support Math Instruction and Student Flourishing? SIG-Research in Mathematics Education; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum A; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Evolving Signals of Quality in K–12 Math Curriculum: A Decade of Field-Based Learning. *Courtney Allison, EdReports; Jake Boesch, EdReports*

The Role of High-Quality Materials in Building Math Coherence. *William McCallum, University of Arizona; April Mouton, Texas State University*

More Than a Swap: Developing Teachers, Assessments, and Planning with New HQIM in Mathematics. *Chris Franklin, Baltimore City Public Schools*

Designing for Enactment: Lessons Learned from Teachers’ Perceptions and Use of HQIM in Mathematics. *Mike Henderson, University of Michigan; Darrius D. Robinson, University of Michigan; Deborah Loewenberg Ball, University of Michigan; Martha Curren-Preis, University of Michigan; Heather Beasley, University of Michigan*

Pedagogical Activism in Mathematics Education During the Civil Rights Movement. *Robert Q. Berry, Indiana University; Casedy A. Thomas, Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University*

Chair: *Darrius D. Robinson, University of Michigan*

Discussants: *Katherine McNeill, Boston College; Denise Walston, Council of the Great City Schools*

26.056. Critical Turn in Teacher Residencies. SIG-School-University Partnership Research; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Georgia II; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Mentoring Antiracist, Antibleist Teachers in Ways that Forefront Antiracism and Antibleism. *Diana Turk, New York University; Rachel Elizabeth Traxler, New York University; Sarah L. Schlessinger, New York University*

Enacting CritPartnership: Centering Criticality in a Teacher Residency Program. *Jori S. Beck, College of William & Mary; Kala Burrell-Craft, Grambling State University*

Three Approaches to Teacher Residencies: A Critical Turn? *Valerie Hill-Jackson, Texas A&M University*

An Abolitionist Teacher Residency. *Stephanie Behm Cross, Georgia State University; Camea Davis, Research Partnership for Professional Learning*

One City One Goal: Preparing Teachers Alongside Community Scholars. *Kay F. Fujiyoshi, University of Chicago*

Chair: *Thomas Albright, Georgia State University*

Discussant: *Naureen Madhani, Columbia University*

26.057. Science and STEM Identity Development and Formation. SIG-Science Teaching and Learning; Paper

Session

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, San Bernardino; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Past, Present and Future of STEM Identity Research: A Bibliometric Analysis. *Tugce Karatas, Purdue University; Andy Parra Martinez, Mississippi State University; Nielsen Pereira, Purdue University/Gifted Education Research & Resource Institute*

Carrying Contextual Learning Experiences Forward: A Structural Equation Model for Youths' STEM Identity Development. *Amdad A. Awsaf, Florida International University; Remy Dou, University of Miami; Sue Sunbury, Harvard University; Gerhard Sonnert, Harvard University; Philip M. Sadler, Harvard University*

Shifting Grounds: Building Science Identity in Geoscience Through Tiered Mentoring. *Virginia W. Snodgrass Rangel, University of Houston; Kelli Lahman, University of Houston; Galo Medina, University of Houston; Tiffany Ngo, University of Houston; Brandee Carlson, University of Houston; Brad Smith, University of Houston; Peter Copeland*

From Inquiry-Based Teaching to Science Career Aspirations: Unequal Motivational Pathways in Western China. *Jiali Li, Shanghai Normal University; Qian Nie, East China Normal University; WenJing Zhang, Shanghai Normal University; Yanan Zhang, Renmin University of China; Wei Wu, Peking University; Huiqing Liang, Henan University; Kai Zhao, Lingnan University*

Echoes of a Pandemic: STEM Students' Science Identity, Belonging, and Self-Efficacy Across Time. *Janet Oluwafunmilola Arogundade, University of North Carolina - Greensboro; Stacy R. Huff, University of North Carolina - Greensboro; Aileen Reid, University of North Carolina - Greensboro; Malcolm Schug, University of North Carolina - Greensboro*

Chair: *Lin Yan, Arizona State University*

26.058. Teaching with Heart and Skill: Exploring Social-Emotional Learning in Teacher Preparation and Practice. SIG-Social and Emotional Learning; Symposium Westin Bonaventure, Level 3, Santa Monica A; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Growth Mindset, Social Emotional Competence, and Early Teaching Experiences: A Longitudinal Experimental Study Using Situational Judgment Tests. *Katharina Asbury, Leibniz Institute for Science and Mathematics Education; Bastian Carstensen, Leibniz Institute for Science and Mathematics Education; Josina Schriek, Humboldt University - Berlin; Uta Klusmann, IPN - Leibniz Institute for Science and Mathematics Education*

Understanding Others' Emotions, Feeling Connected: How Teachers' Social-Emotional Competence Links to Occupational Well-Being. *Josina Schriek, Humboldt*

University - Berlin; Bastian Carstensen, Leibniz Institute for Science and Mathematics Education; Katharina Asbury, Leibniz Institute for Science and Mathematics Education; Uta Klusmann, IPN - Leibniz Institute for Science and Mathematics Education

Results of a Randomized Controlled Trial of RULER: Impact on Teacher and Classroom Outcomes. *Sara E. Rimm-Kaufman, University of Virginia; Xavier Elzie, University of Virginia; Jason Downer, University of Virginia; Jamie DeCoster, University of Virginia; Lee Leboeuf, University of Virginia*

Lessons from Kōwhiri Whakapae in Aotearoa New Zealand: Strengthening Practice to Support Progress or Strengthening Progress Through Practice, And Does it Matter? *Tara McLaughlin, Massey University*

Chairs: *Katharina Asbury, Leibniz Institute for Science and Mathematics Education; Josina Schriek, Humboldt University - Berlin*

Discussant: *Patricia A. Jennings, University of Virginia*

26.059. Rethinking Teacher-AI Partnerships in Lesson Planning and Assessment. SIG-Technology as an Agent of Change in Teaching and Learning; Paper Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum I; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Co-creating Knowledge with GenAI: Shared Epistemic Agency and Critical AI Literacy in K-12 Lesson Planning. *Yingru Zhao, University at Albany - SUNY; Jaesung Park, University at Albany - SUNY; Devan Walton, University at Albany - SUNY; Haesol Bae, University at Albany - SUNY; Dongni Guo, University at Albany - SUNY*

Innovation or Imitation? Analyzing AI-Generated Lesson Plans for Technology Integration. *Chenyang Xu, University of Massachusetts - Amherst; Torrey Trust, University of Massachusetts - Amherst; Robert Maloy, University of Massachusetts - Amherst; Kael Pelletier, University of Massachusetts - Amherst*

Mathematics Learning Task Quality in Teacher-GenAI Collaboration: Assessment and Success Factors. *Jie Cao, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Shuman Wang, Stanford University; Christian D. Schunn, University of Pittsburgh*

Chair: *Lei Wang, Auburn University - Montgomery*

Discussant: *Ruthmae Sears, University of South Florida*

26.060. AI-Enhanced Student Learning Outcomes. SIG-Technology, Instruction, Cognition & Learning; Paper Session Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, San Gabriel B; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

A Meta-Review of AI-Powered Chatbots and Their Impact on Learning Outcomes. *Secil Caskurlu, Florida State*

University; Huan Kuang, Florida State University; Seungjie Clarice Han, Florida State University

Effect of Generative AI on Undergraduates' Learning Outcomes: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis.

Shuzhen Chen, Chinese University of Hong Kong

The effects of human-technology interaction on engineering students' learning outcomes: A multilevel meta-analysis.

Ying Liang, 浙江大学, Yan Li, Zhejiang University

The impact of teacher presence on student engagement with artificial intelligence chatbots in language learning.

Yan LI, The Education University of Hong Kong; Yuanyuan WU, Jiangsu University; Thomas K.F. Chiu, The Chinese University of Hong Kong

Enhancing Student Learning through Generative AI: A Five-Year Systematic Review of Higher Education Research.

Ayesha Sadaf, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Katherine Jiawen Ren, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Judson Macdonald, University of North Carolina at Charlotte; Delandrus Lenet Ieashea Seales, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Ji Yae Bong, University of North Carolina - Charlotte

Chair: Idowu David Awoyemi, University of Alabama

Discussant: Anastasia Shikanova, The Ohio State University

26.061. Speculative Futures with and Against AI: Youth Worldbuilding as Sociotechnical Intervention. SIG-Writing and Literacies; Symposium

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Atrium II; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Ideating Worlds with ChatGPT: Critical Inquiries into the Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Narrative Composing.

Alex Corbitt, Syracuse University

High School Students as Designers of Generative Language Models. Luis Morales-Navarro, University of Pennsylvania; Daniel J Noh, University of Pennsylvania; Yasmin B. Kafai, University of Pennsylvania

Re-imagining AI-Human Relationships in World-Building Contexts through Everyday Movement. Michael Alan Chang, Boston University; Beth M. Warren, Boston University; Gia Kim, Boston University; Heila Prezel, Boston University

Speculating AI's "Second Life": Youth's Carnavalesque (Re)Writing with AI. Rabani Garg, University of Pennsylvania; Clara Abbott, University of Pennsylvania; Amy Stornaiuolo, University of Pennsylvania

Chairs: Rabani Garg, University of Pennsylvania; Clara Abbott, University of Pennsylvania

Discussant: Tiera C. Tanksley, University of Colorado - Boulder

Division and SIG Roundtables

26.062. AERA Roundtable Session Wednesday 3:45 pm;

Roundtable Session

26.062-1. Women Redefining Educational Leadership (Table 1). Division A - Administration; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Women High School Principals: Perspectives on Negotiating Their Gendered Role. Anne Allegretti, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign

How do female school leaders perceive and navigate their leadership roles and personal self-care practices? Prattasha Paul, St. John's University

Radical Maternidad: Latina School Leaders' Testimonios of Agency, Care, and Resilience in Times of Crisis. Jennifer Ventimiglia, Northeastern Illinois University

Overcoming Obstacles in the Pursuit of the Superintendency. Monica Headen, East Carolina University

Chair: Jennie Weiner, University of Connecticut

26.062-2. The Flow State: When Leadership Work Meets Well-Being Matters (Table 2). Division A - Administration; Roundtable Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Conceptualizing Dialogic Leadership Through a Relational Worldview: Human Revolution, Dialogue and Invitational Rhetoric. Nitesh Sil, DIG International; Melissa Riley Bradford, DePaul University

Investigating the Significance of Flow Experiences for the Well-Being and Retention of School Principals. Samuel P. Whalen, University of Illinois at Chicago

26.062-3. Navigating Structural Inequalities with Social and Technical Networks (Table 3). Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

AI Tools are Learning with Us: Newcomer Families' Sensemaking of GenAI, Language, and Identity. Silvia C. Noguero-Liu, University of Colorado - Boulder; Paula Bernal, University of Colorado - Boulder; Stephany Cáceres-Mateo, University of Colorado - Boulder; Tania Hogan, University of Colorado - Boulder

Class Ceiling: Examining the Association Between Social Class Discrimination and Academic Outcomes Among Latine Adolescents. Abraham Tou Jang Moua, San Francisco State University; Jo Nisa Cabilogan, San Francisco State University; Jeremiah Sabale, San Francisco State University; Manuel Abundis-Morales, San Francisco State University; Adam Suri, San Francisco State University; Busra Dogru, San Francisco State University; Jay Espinoza,

San Francisco State University; Bingyue Tan, San Francisco State University; Dania Smith, San Francisco State University; Dolci Winer, University of San Francisco; Stella Sears-Bicknell, Oberlin College; Felicia Deshon, University of California - Los Angeles; Zena R. Mello, San Francisco State University

Social Capital and Educational Success in Vulnerable Contexts: A Mixed-Methods Study. *Maria Vilas, Ramon Llull University; Jordi Riera, Ramon Llull University; Elena Carrillo Alvarez, Ramon Llull University*

Systemic Inequities in Access to Arts Education: A School-Level Analysis of U.S. Secondary Schools. *day parker, University of Michigan*

Reclaiming Voice: Examining Student Power, Participation, and Identity Through Engagement with and Leadership in Student Ambassador Councils. *Stacy E. Ellis, Avondale Elementary School District; Audrey Amrein-Beardsley, Arizona State University*

Chair: *Silvia C. Nogueron-Liu, University of Colorado - Boulder*

26.062-4. Racialization, State Power, and Resilience: Comparative Perspectives on National Education Systems (Table 4).

Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Defining Muslim Racialization in US Schools: A Post-9/11 Systematic Literature Review. *Miriam Deborah Ezzani, Texas Christian University; Melanie Carol Brooks, Edith Cowan University; Stephanie Cuellar, Texas Christian University; Camille Austin Henderson, Texas Christian University*

How Districts Differ: Understanding Black Student Academic Growth Across U.S. Districts. *Darnell Leatherwood, University of Michigan; Faeze Safari, University of Connecticut; Jennifer Aracely Rodriguez, University of Michigan Ann Arbor*

How National Contexts Predict and Shape Students' Digital Literacy: A Multilevel Analysis of ICILS 2023. *Minju Kim, Korea University; Beilei Gou, Korea University; Pey-Yan Liou, Korea University*

Social Unrest, State Control, and the Birth of Educational Bureaucracy in the British Empire. *Faith D. Northern, New York University*

Uncovering the Invisible: A Multidimensional Framework for Identifying Resilient Students across Different Countries and Grades. *QIAN LI, Beijing Normal University; Yiwen Dong, Beijing Normal University*

Chair: *Darnell Leatherwood, University of Michigan*

26.062-5. Educational Research on Humanizing Pedagogy (Table 5).

Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Mindfulness as Justice: Empathy, Harm Reduction, and Empowerment in K12 Spaces. *Kazumi Igus, Claremont Graduate University*

Transformative hospitality: A pedagogical framework for reimagining educational experience. *Eric Alvarez, Arizona State University; Roya Fathalizadeh, Arizona State University*

Equity Beyond Compliance: Humanizing Education in the Shadow of a Polycrisis. *Dionne L. Davis, Texas State University; Emily Faulkner, Texas State University; Shantelle A. Quintana, Texas State University; Erica Shoulders-Royster, North Carolina State University; Jen Davis, Texas State University*

From Resistance to Restoration: Advancing Culturally Responsive School Leadership Toward Collective Liberation and Transformative Movement. *Lewis F. Thomas, Monmouth University*

Chair: *Érica Fernández, Miami University (OH)*

26.062-6. Equitable Community Partnership for Educational Research (Table 6).

Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Beneath and Beyond: Informal Networks as the Undercommons of Immigrant Youth's Postsecondary Pathways. *Lauren McCoy, Hunter College; Jordan Corson, Stockton University*

Family and Community Engagement as a Key Driver of Reduced Chronic Absenteeism in Community Schools. *Dandan Yang, University of California - Los Angeles; Nadia M. Sabat Bass, University of California - Los Angeles; Marisa Saunders, University of California - Los Angeles*

Re-envisioning University-Community Relations: The Problem with Partnership, Educational Equity, and Mutual Benefit. *Christopher Hu, University of Alabama*

Spectral Presence and Community Preservation: Examining the Historical Development of Principal Preparation Programs Through a Genealogical Analysis. *Karina Flores-Camacho, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Chair: *Xin Li, University of Houston*

26.062-7. Technology and Adolescent and Youth Development (Table 7).

SIG-Adolescence and Youth Development; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Digital Refuge or Digital Stress? How Perceived Usefulness of LLMs Reshape Academic Anxiety Through Identity and Self-Efficacy Pathways. *Wencan Li, East China Normal*

University; Xingchen Zhu, Liaoning Normal University
Latent Profiles of Smartphone Use Among the Chinese Left-behind Adolescents: Associations with Psychological Well-being, Academic Expectations, and Behavioral Tendencies. Wangqian Fu, Beijing Normal University; Guanyu Chen, University of British Columbia

Learning in the Layers: Adolescent Routines and Development in a Digital Ecological System. Vanessa Dennen, Florida State University; Idam Kim, Florida State University; Melissa K. Jones, Dartmouth College

The Impact of Group Discrimination on Smartphone Addiction : A Research Using Data from China. Shutao Wang, Xiamen University; Liu Jingjing, Xiamen University

Title: Who's at Risk? A Latent Class Analysis of Problematic Mobile Gaming, Depression, and Self-Harm in Adolescents Experiencing Traditional Bullying, Cyberbullying, and Sexting. Shan-Mei Chang, Tsinghua University; Jo-Chi Hsiao, National Yang Ming Chiao Tung University; Yu-Hsuan Lin, National Health Research Institutes of Taiwan; Wan-Chen Lee, Taipei City Hospital Renai Branch of Taiwan

26.062-8. Bourdieu and Teacherly Dispositions (Table 8). SIG-Bourdieu in Educational Research; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Divergent Realities: A Bourdieusian Narrative Inquiry into Professional Identity and Opportunity in Canadian EAP/TESOL. Aylar Akeh, Simon Fraser University

Negotiating Legitimacy: Chinese Language Teachers' Identity Formation in Culturally Stratified International Schools in Hong Kong. Warangkana Lin, I-Shou University

The influence of Institutional Epistemological Beliefs and Teachers' Epistemological Dispositions on Classroom Practices. Thomas Gennen, University of California, Berkeley

26.062-9. Semiotics in Education: Signs, Meanings and Multimodality Roundtable Sessions (Table 9). SIG-Semiotics in Education: Signs, Meanings and Multimodality; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

From Educational Term to Cultural Symbol: The Semiotic Evolution of "Chinese-Style Education" Discourse. Jingjing Yang, East China Normal University

Understanding the Digital Literacies Profile of Students in Singapore and China: Implications for Teacher Education. Jia'en Yee, Nanyang Technological University - National Institute of Education; Fei Victor Lim, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University; Cong Xu, London School of Economics and Political Science

Visual Artifacts as Scaffolds in Multilingual Third-grade Classrooms: How Do Visual Scaffolds Support Engineering and Translanguaging. Mary B. McVee, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Jessica Swenson, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Duncan Mullins, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Dameeni Lagad, University at Buffalo - SUNY; YueQiu Zhang, University at Buffalo - SUNY

26.062-10. Thriving Futures: Opening Career Pathways Through Out of School Time Experiences (Table 10).

SIG-Out-of-School Time; Roundtable Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Career-Connected Learning in Out-of-School Time: Teen Science Cafes and STEM Pathways. Breanna Jones, STEM Next Opportunity Fund; Jessica Sickler, J. Sickler Consulting; Andria Parrott, STEM Next Opportunity Fund; Katey Ahmann, STEM Next Opportunity Fund

Developing STEM Career Goals in Urban High Schools? Evidence from an Experimental Algebra-for-Engineering Afterschool Program. Alexis Daniels, Johns Hopkins University; Rachel E. Durham, Notre Dame of Maryland University

Teaching Fellows to Teachers: How Out-of-School Programs can Recruit and Retain Educators. Chloe Fann, University of Memphis; Jennifer R. Renick, Michigan State University; Natalie Jacobs Hall, Breakthrough Collaborative; Jeehye Deogracias, Breakthrough Collaborative

Discussant: Charmaine Davis-Grant, Department of Education and Workforce (DEW)

26.063. AERA Roundtable Session Wednesday 3:45 pm - Gold 1; Roundtable Session

26.063-1. Teaching Truth in Turbulent Times: Navigating Controversy, Civic Courage, and Historical Reckoning in Education (Table 1). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

From Participation to Disruption: A Critical Curriculum Inquiry into Political Friendship and Civic Education Reform. Shuning Liu, Ball State University; Eli Jones, Ball State University

"I Will Never Teach January 6": Teachers' Ecological Considerations in Teaching Difficult Histories. Amy Chell Stell, University of Rochester; Rebecca Rosen, Princeton University; Mary Maslanka; Luke Hands, University of Rochester; Kevin W. Meuwissen, University of Rochester
Preparing Teachers to Lead Digital Source Credibility Discussions about Contentious Civic Issues. Elizabeth Reynolds, University of Maryland

Teaching Controversy in the Classroom: A Systematic Review of Challenges, Teacher Positions, and Strategies in Teaching Controversial Issues. *Yue Li, The Chinese University of Hong Kong*

“We should tell students they were gay?”: Pre-service teachers reckon with authenticity and truthful narratives in teaching the American Revolution. *Brian C. Gibbs, Georgia College & State University*

Chair: *Shuning Liu, Ball State University*

26.063-2. Teacher Advocacy and Activism to Transgress: Centering Ethnic and Linguistic Identities (Table 2).

Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Activist Travels: Two Mexican-Origin Teachers’ Transgressions Across Racial Geographies. *Andrew Hilton Hurie, University of Wisconsin - Whitewater; Juan F. Carrillo, Arizona State University*

Language↔Space↔Identity in Practice: Translanguaging and Teacher Agency in Multilingual Classrooms. *Seongryeong Yu, Old Dominion University; Sung Ryung Lyu, American University; Kiyomi Umezawa, University of Hawai’i at Manoa*

Lessons in Sustainable Advocacy From English Language Development Educators. *Olivia E. Obeso, California Polytechnic State University - San Luis Obispo*

We Are Not Neutral: Latinx Literacy Leaders Fostering a Circle of Hope. *Madeleine Mejia, California State University - Fullerton; Laura Keisler, California State University - Fullerton; Rosario M. Ordonez-Jasis, California State University - Fullerton*

Chair: *Carolina Valdez, California State University - Fullerton*

26.063-3. Teacher Education at the Crossroads: Critical Praxis, Policy, and Possibility (Table 3).

Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Critical Race Praxis in English Language Teacher Education: Translating Critical Awareness into Concrete Transformation. *Abdulmalik Abiola Salman, The University of Alabama*

Exploring The Role of Race and Deficit/Asset Narratives in Teachers’ Integration of Student FoK. *Kamil Hankour, Virginia Commonwealth University; Rachel Niemira, Virginia Commonwealth University; Ryan LeVault, Virginia Commonwealth University; Singith Nuwanga Perera, Virginia Commonwealth University; Gabriella Osei-Poku, Virginia Commonwealth University; Christine Lee Bae, Virginia Commonwealth University*

First Stop, Panajachel: The Role of Transformative Experience for ESOL Educators. *James Coda, University of Tennessee; Liv H. Detwiler, East Tennessee State University; Felipe Trevisan Ferreira, University of Tennessee*

“I Don’t Want to Get in Trouble”: Preservice Teachers’ Sensemaking of Undocumented Status Under Policy Constraint. *Jennifer M. Bondy, Arizona State University*
Professional Learning Design for Rural Elementary Teachers on Advocacy for Transgender Students. *Jana Stone, Fort Lewis College; Sharon B. Hayes, West Virginia University*

Chair: *Larry C. Bryant, Metro State University*

Discussant: *Larry C. Bryant, Metro State University*

26.063-4. Supervision and Social Justice: Supporting Preservice Teachers’ Growth, Agency, and Critical Reflections on Power (Table 4).

Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Empowering STEM Educators for Social Justice: The AAA Model for Teacher Education and Supervision. *Stephanie A. Arthur, University of South Florida; Allan Feldman, University of South Florida*

Engaging in Innovative and Equitable PST Education Practices and Enacting Social Justice Pedagogy in Liminal Spaces. *Maggie Mnayer, Central Michigan University; Alice N. Williams, Florida State University*

“I don’t need permission to create change”: Affirming and Advancing Teacher Candidates’ Racial Micropolitical Literacies. *Acelynn C. Perkins, University of Colorado - Boulder; Brenda Ortiz Torres, University of Colorado - Boulder*

Supervising for Social Justice: University Supervisor Practices that Support Pre-Service Teacher Growth. *Lindsay J. Wexler, North Central College*

Chair: *Harper B. Keenan, University of British Columbia*

26.063-5. Honoring Languages, Ethics, and Global Futures: Reimagining Teacher Education for Justice (Table 5).

Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Do-v-Da: A card game to help teachers practice engaging with ethical pedagogical dilemmas. *Gautam Singh Bisht, Northwestern University; Vishesh Kumar, Northwestern University; Khushbu Kshirsagar, Northwestern University*

Lessons from Los Angeles: The Impact of Global Citizenship Education Course and its Implications for Research and Practice. *Fadhila Hadjeris, University of California - Los Angeles; Nancy Yaxiang Xu, University of California - Los Angeles*

Pretouguês Meets AAVE: Blackiguês and Language Embodiment in the Multilingual Classroom. *Mariane de Araujo Batista-McCulloch, University of Minnesota*
Redesigning Credential Programs: Supporting Emergent Plurilingual Students Through Linguistic Justice. *Kira LeeKeenan, California State University - Fullerton; Fernando Rodriguez-Valls, California State University - Fullerton; Gavin Tierney, California State University - Fullerton*

Chair: *Sabahet S. Bruncaj, United Arab Emirates University*

26.063-6. From Partnership to Practice: RPPs, Pathways, and Program Innovation (Table 6). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Educator Development Research-Practice Partnerships: Developing a Measurement Tool for Collective Learning, Investigation, and Liberation. *Conra D. Gist, University of Houston; Maggie Hannan, WestEd*

Knowledge Generation, Transfer, Exchange, and Production in School-University Partnerships in China: Stakeholder Perspectives. *Wanyue Chen, University of Nottingham*

Preservice Teachers' Uses of Content and Pedagogical Content Knowledge in Lesson Plans and Lessons on Energy. *Yanhong Moore, McGregor Independent School District; Jian Wang, Texas Tech University*

Strategies and Challenges in Developing Computer Science Teacher Preparation Pathways. *Erin Anderson, Georgia State University; Yin-Chan Janet Liao, Georgia State University; Ijeoma Mbaezue, Georgia State University; Jennifer Rosato, University of Minnesota; Michelle Friend, University of Nebraska - Omaha*

The Student and Teacher Educational Partnership (STEP) Model in Higher Education. *Wajiha Masroor, Texas A&M University; Mahjabin Chowdhury, Texas A&M University; Kati I. Stoddard, Texas A&M University*

Chair: *Conra D. Gist, University of Houston*

26.063-7. From Courtrooms to Classrooms: The Politics of Reform (Table 7). Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Big P and Little P Politics: Contemporary and Enduring Challenges for K-12 School Board Members. *Julie A. Marsh, University of Southern California; Jeimee Estrada-Miller, University of Southern California; Beth Schueler, University of Virginia*

Education Without Borders: Archival Insights into the Enduring Impact of Plyler v. Doe. *Jacqueline White, Texas A&M University*

Looking Back to Move Forward: Leading Schools for Equity by Historicizing Educational Crisis. *M. Nathan Tanner, University of Nevada - Reno; Christopher J. Getowicz, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*
More Than a Seat at the Table: Reimagining Power and Participation in K-12 Educational Governance. *Mikah Dyer, Arizona State University; Tara Lynn Bartlett, Arizona State University*

Navigating Education Reform: Understanding China's Double Reduction Policy in Practice Through Stephen Ball's Policy Circle. *Sini Wu, University of Manchester*

Chair: *Lori D. Rhea, University of Houston*

Discussant: *Jawanza Kalonji Rand, Teachers College, Columbia University*

26.063-8. Unequal Returns: How Policy Shapes Learning, Inequality, and Social Mobility (Table 8). Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Educational Governance and Skills Inequality: Evidence from Chile, Finland, and the U.S. *Francisca Beroiza-Valenzuela, Universidad de las Américas (UDLA), Chile; Daniela Véliz Calderón, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile*

How Does China's Higher Education Expansion Policy Affect Income Inequality? An Empirical Test. *Tianyi Sun, East China Normal University; Chunshun Yan, East China Normal University*

The Effects of Kindergarten Entry Age on Academic Achievement. *NaYoung Hwang, University of New Hampshire; Christopher Redding, University of Florida*

Time-Poor Teachers: Analyzing the impact of antithetical Accountability using TALIS 2018. *Dahee Shin, Seoul National University; Moonyoung Eom, Seoul National University*

Texas College, Career, and Military Readiness Standards and Student Achievement of a Self-Sufficiency Standard Wage. *Molly E. Cain, American Institutes for Research; Kristina L. Zeiser, American Institutes for Research*

Chair: *NaYoung Hwang, University of New Hampshire*

26.064. AERA Roundtable Session Wednesday 3:45 pm - Gold 2; Roundtable Session

26.064-1. Curricular Resources for Mathematics: Friends or Foes? (Table 1). SIG-Research in Mathematics Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Examining Fidelity of Implementation in an Early Algebra Effectiveness Study. *Despina A. Stylianou, City College of New York - CUNY; Maria Blanton, TERC; Barbara M.*

Brizuela, Tufts University; Angela Gardiner, TERC; Mathias Agustin Lopez, Tufts University; Nicole Shields, The City University of New York; Susanne Strachota, Tufts University; Rena Stroud, Merrimack College

Operationalized Criteria For Textbook Analysis: Using Cognitive Demand Level Framework. Boram Lee, Utah State University; Seyedehkhadijeh Azimi Asmaroud, Virginia State University

Textbook, Teacher, and AI-Generated Word Problems and Third Graders' Evaluations of Them. Laura Bofferding, Purdue University; Yi Zhu, Purdue University; Sezai Kocabas, Bilkent University

The Impact of the Illustrative Math Curriculum on Middle School Math Achievement. Noman Khanani, WestEd; Kirk Walters, WestEd; Rebecca R. Perry, WestEd

Making Sense of Curriculum Change: Supporting Teacher Sensemaking Through Professional Learning. Margaret T Ellis, University of Delaware; Kelly A. McKie, University of Delaware; Erica Litke, University of Delaware; Lynsey K. Gibbons, University of Delaware; James Hiebert, University of Delaware

Chair: Madeleine Kingan, Harvard University

26.064-2. Embracing Creativity and Play in the Teaching and Learning of Mathematics (Table 2). SIG-Research in Mathematics Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Beyond Balance: Dynamic Interactions and Mathematical Learning in a Play-based Kindergarten Classroom. Jingyi Chen, Vanderbilt University

Mathematical Creativity as a Unifying Lens: A Case Study of Instructional Shifts in Elementary Classrooms Through Sustained Professional Development. Ali Bicer, Texas A&M University; Fay S. Quiroz, University of Wyoming; Aysenur Bicer, Texas A&M University; Tugce Aldemir, Texas A&M University; Micayla Gooden, Texas A&M University; Zulal Melek, Iowa State University

Productive Mathematical Dispositions and Curricular Creativity: Sharing Mathematicians' Stories in K-12 Classrooms. Nasriah Morrison, Teachers College, Columbia University; Terika Harris, Teachers College, Columbia University; Nicole Fletcher, Fairfield University; Erica N. Walker, University of Toronto - OISE; Robin Wilson, Loyola Marymount University; Anisha Clarke, Queens College - CUNY; Nathan Dilworth, Teachers College, Columbia University

Supporting Mathematical Creative Development through Dialogic Assessment. Meghan Riling, Vanderbilt University
Teaching and Learning with Nondigital Fraction Games. Jenny Goldberg, University of California - Santa Barbara; Rachel Lambert, University of California - Santa Barbara

Chair: Lybrya Kebreab, California State University - Pomona

26.064-3. Identity development and support networks among STEM college students and professionals from non-dominant communities (Table 3). SIG-Socio-Political Issues in Mathematics and Science Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Navigating Research Pathways: The Role of Social Networks in Latinx STEM Students' Access to Undergraduate Research Opportunities. Katherine Arias Garcia, University of California - Irvine

Navigating STEM Fields: How Historically Marginalized Professionals Construct Disciplinary Identities Through Bourdieu's Theory of Practice. Ufomanefe Shola Kayode, Texas Tech University; Weverton Ataíde Pinheiro, Texas Tech University; Joshua M. Cruz, Texas Tech University; Fatimah Rabi'u, Texas Tech University; Rachelle M. Pedersen, Texas Tech University; Isiaka Ayobi Raheem, Texas Tech University; Adedayo Olatunde Afolabi, Texas Tech University

STEM Identity Negotiations of First-Generation Latinas. Rocío Vaneza Quiroga Velasquez, George Mason University
The Role of Cultural Expectations in Middle Eastern/North African Students' Mathematics Identity. Sara Mia Elakesh, Michigan State University

26.064-4. Leadership, Policy, and Practice in Inclusive and Special Education (Table 4). SIG-Special and Inclusive Education Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Inclusive Leadership Is Not Optional: Why Principal Prep Must Change. Catherine E. Olver, Gonzaga University

What's Missing? Reviewing Conceptual Discourse of Inclusive Education in Indonesia. Ikfina Maufuriyah, Indiana University

Held in Contradiction: What Special Educators Report—and What They Really Say. Katherine Lee, Saint Michael's College

Chair: Catherine Kramarczuk Voulgarides, Hunter College - CUNY

26.064-5. Pathways to Independence: Postsecondary Experiences for Students with Disabilities (Table 5). SIG-Special and Inclusive Education Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Navigating Postsecondary Possibilities for Students with Intellectual Disabilities: Case Manager Perspectives. Sarah

Dubin, Rowan University

Looking Back, Moving Forward: Pre-HEOA Inclusive Postsecondary Education and the Road Ahead. *Sara Jo Hoffdovieri, The IDEAL School; Beth Myers, Syracuse University*

Faculty Insights on Teaching Self-Determination Skills in Postsecondary Education to Students with/without Disabilities. *Jacqueline Lubin, Quinnipiac University*

Mismatched to Needs and Not Evidence-Based: A Literature Review of Postsecondary Autistic Student Supports. *Amy Hoffman, University of California - Riverside; Katherine Meltzoff, University of California - Riverside*

26.064-6. Navigating Belonging & Identity: Diverse Doctoral Journeys (Table 6). SIG-Graduate and Postdoctoral Education across the Disciplines; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

A Narrative Inquiry into International Doctoral Students' Emotional Experiences in Navigating Their Researcher Identity Development. *Ngoc Kim Tuyen Pham, Texas Tech University; Jeasik Cho, Texas Tech University*

Becoming Researchers Together: Mentorship, Identity, and Belonging in an Online Graduate Research Collective. *Laila Y. Sanguras, Baylor University; Heather Bailie Schock, University of Tampa; Rachel Coussens, Baylor University; Norm Reinhardt, Baylor University; Kerstin Marie Cornell, Baylor University; Melissa J. Allen, Alpine School District*

Self-perceived identities of female doctoral students in mobility: Empowered transformation or eroding academic commitment? *Jialu Wang, Peking University; Fengyi Lin, Peking University; Wenqin Shen, Peking University*

Sense of Belonging: A Longitudinal Study of Minority Engineering Doctoral Students. *Mayra S Artiles, The Ohio State University; Jordan Peyton, Ohio State University; Rachel Figard, University of Georgia; Holly M. Matusovich, Virginia Tech; Juan Manuel Cruz, Rowan University; Stephanie G. Adams, University of Texas at Dallas*

Unsettling Silences: Exploring Imposter Syndrome Among African International PhD Students and Its Implications for Belonging, Integration, and Academic Self-Efficacy. *Mohammed Ibrahim, Arizona State University*

26.064-7. Language Ideologies, Power, Resistance in Educational Spaces (Table 7). SIG-Language and Social Processes; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

"It would have only taken 527 different votes." Analyzing Justifications for English as Official Language. *Kate Arnold*
Deconstructing dominant listening practices in oral language assessment settings. *Juan Bueno Holle, California State*

University - Sacramento; Nadxieli Toledo Bustamante, California State University - Sacramento

Trapped by The System: An Analysis of Resistance to EL Re-Categorization. *Maneka Deanna Brooks, Portland State University; Katherine C. Rodela, Washington State University*

Whose Benefit? Disrupting Discourses on DEI and the Positioning of Racialized International Graduate Students. *Tanya R. Manning-Lewis, Thompson Rivers University*

Applying a Critical Discourse Analysis to Reimagine Classroom Participation. *Jonathan Desmon Russell Pérez, The School of The New York Times*

Chair: *Audrey Lucero, University of Oregon*

26.064-8. Literacies of Care, Culture, and Community (Table 8). SIG-Language and Social Processes; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

The Role of Korean Church in Korean American Youth's Cultural and Linguistic Identity Development. *Hye-In Yang, Michigan State University*

Encountering Diversity through Young Adult Literature: Preservice Teachers' Empathic Engagement in Book Club Discussions. *Kwangok Song, University of Kansas; SoonAh Lee, Gwangju National University of Education*

Centering and Amplifying Asian American Histories and Voices in Dual Language Bilingual Education. *Wenyu Guo, University of South Florida; Zhongfeng Tian, Rutgers University - Newark*

Chair: *Kwangok Song, University of Kansas*

26.064-9. Culturally Sustaining and Decolonial Pedagogies: Transforming Indigenous Education Through Community-Driven Research and Educational Reform (Table 9). SIG-Indigenous Peoples of the Americas; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Embracing Critical Literacy Epistemology: Honoring Histories through Culturally Sustaining Pedagogies. *Isela Almaguer, University of Texas - Rio Grande Valley*

Implementing Indigenous Studies Curriculum Standards: Case Studies of a Complicated Curricular Process. *Sage Hatch, University of Oregon*

Navigating the Education of Indigenous Students in Rural Schools: Toward Culturally Responsive Practices Across Educational Levels. *Cailen O'Shea, North Dakota State University; Amber M. O'Shea, University of Nebraska - Omaha; Sashay Schettler, Bismark Public Schools; Hollie Mackey, North Dakota State University*

Results of the New Mexico Native American Capstone and Graduation Profile Study: Leveraging Edu-Local Goals and

Values. *Wendy S Greyeyes, University of New Mexico; Kim Lanoy-Sandoval, Future Focused Education; Lisa Harmon-Martínez, Future Focused Education*

Discussant: *Patience Amadu, University of Colorado - Colorado Springs*

26.065. AERA Roundtable Session Wednesday 3:45 pm - Gold 3; Roundtable Session

26.065-1. Biographical Stories, Cultural Preservation, and Creative Research Practices in Education (Table 1). SIG-Biographical and Documentary Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

“Die Deutsche Stunde:” The Pioneering Pedagogy of Ilse Edse’s German Educational Television and Radio Programs.

Kyle J. Williams, The Ohio State University

Learning From Archival Biographical Research: Flora Carncross -Missionary and Principal During the Chinese Revolution [1908-1925]. *Karen E. Watkins, University of Georgia; Tanya DaMommio, Texas State University; Victoria J. Marsick, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Tracing Reform Through Biography: Philipp Schwartz and the Academic Diaspora in Türkiye (1933-1945). *Seyma Aksoy, Yıldız Technical University Türkiye*

Speculative Possibilities for Black Life in the Academy.

Candace N. Hall, Southern Illinois University - Edwardsville; Charles H.F. Davis, University of Michigan; Christopher S. Travers, University of Maryland

Unforgetting Contributions to Environmental Preservation: Remembering Elzada Clover’s and Lois Jotter’s Historical Journey and Work. *Margaret-Mary Sulentic Dowell, Louisiana State University; Hayley Alyce Graham, Louisiana State University*

Chair: *Margaret-Mary Sulentic Dowell, Louisiana State University*

26.065-2. School and community leadership and engagement (Table 2). SIG-Family, School, Community Partnerships; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

The Role and Participation Dynamics of Parent-Guardian Associations (PGAs). *Maria Savva, European University Cyprus; Loizos Symeou, European University Cyprus*

Cross Cultural Validation of the School Cultural Congruity Scale: A Cross-National Study. *Lakhvir Kaur, University of California - Santa Barbara; Shane R. Jimerson, University of California - Santa Barbara; Kelly-Ann Allen, Monash University; Chryse (Sissy) Hatzichristou, National & Kapodistrian, University of Athens, Greece*

District-Level Implementation of Community Schools:

Learnings from a Research Practice Partnership for Continuous Improvement. *Ana Ventura-Molina, American University; Kecia Hayes, American University; Robert Shand, American University; Reuben Jacobson, American University*

Community as Curriculum: A Case Study in Courageous Leadership and the Politics of Equity. *Joan Schumann, International MTSS Association*

Chair: *Gal Harpaz, The Open University of Israel*

26.065-3. Meditation, Mindfulness, and Educational Transformation (Table 3). SIG-Holistic Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Cultivating Loving-Kindness in Future Educational Leaders: A Qualitative Study of Practicing Meditation with Doctorate of Education Students. *Steven Haberman, University of Central Florida; David N. Boote, University of Central Florida; Terrie Bradshaw, University of Central Florida*

Honoring Neurodiversity by Exploring Undergraduates’ Individual Preferences for Meditation Methods. *Steven Haberman, University of Central Florida; Shiva Jahani, University of Central Florida*

Holistic Chinese Traditional Indigenous Sports into the Holistic Development of Young People: Theory and Practice. *zhixing Xu, Guangxi University*

Placing Happiness at the Center of Education. *Tiaotiao Qian, Zhejiang University*

Taming Anxiety: Integrating Equine-Assisted Learning and Peer Mentorship to Support Rural Adolescent Mental Health. *Lauren Davis, Montana State University; Christine Stanton, Montana State University*

Chair: *Cassandra Victoria Guzman, Cornell University*

Discussant: *Kavya Sree Mariboyina, Little Priest Tribal College*

26.065-4. Rethinking Qualitative Research in Virtual Spaces: Ethics, Inclusion, and Methodological Adaptation (Table 4). Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

A Qualitative Approach to Document Analysis. *Hani Morgan, University of Southern Mississippi*

Reimagining qualitative interviews using Microsoft Teams in Jamaican educational research. *Delta Wright, Edge Hill University*

Detecting and responding to imposter participants in online interview studies: Collaborative decision-making and solutions. *Audra Skukauskaitė, University of Central Florida; Stephanie Couch, Massachusetts Institute of Technology; Tamara Galoyan, Massachusetts Institute of*

Technology

Chair: *Hani Morgan, University of Southern Mississippi*

26.065-5. Story, Trace, and Resistance: Arts-Based and Culturally Rooted Interventions in Qualitative Research (Table 5). Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

A Way of Knowing: Iyagi as a Qualitative Research Framework to Understand Bilingual Children. *Pyeongun Kim, Michigan State University*

Zine-making as Slow Scholarship: A Critical Qualitative Intervention. *Sharla Berry, California State University - Long Beach*

26.065-6. Computational Assessment in Education: Validity Evidence from Automation to Adaptivity (Table 6). Division H - Research, Evaluation and Assessment in Schools; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Automated Extraction of Computational Thinking Features in Visual Programming Assessment. *Yishen Song, Beijing Normal University*

Computer Scoring of a Visual Motor Assessment. *Randy Fall, Azusa Pacific University*

Measuring Learning and Knowledge Coherence in Student Reasoning about Matter and Energy Using the MOMO Instrument. *Austin Zuckerman, Cornell University; Ross H. Nehm, Stony Brook University - SUNY; Gena Sbeglia, San Diego State University*

The Criterion-Related Validity and Classification Accuracy of Computer Adaptive Testing on Reading: A Meta-Analysis. *Linling Shen, University of Texas at Austin; Yixian Huang, University of Texas at Austin; Zixuan Ma, University of Texas at Austin; Man Chen, University of Texas at Austin; Nathan H. Clemens, University of Texas at Austin*

Chair: *Walter M. Stroup, University of Massachusetts - Dartmouth*

26.065-7. Perspectives on Leadership and Systemic Change in Health Professions (Table 7). Division I - Education in the Professions; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

A Systematic Literature Review: The Affordable Care Act and Physician Job Satisfaction, after Medicare Expansion. *Kaitlin Rogers, University of Oklahoma; Julianna E. Lopez Kershen, University of Oklahoma*

Leveraging Physician-Scientist Caregiver Insights for Institutional Planning and Systemic Change Management.

Kadian McIntosh, University of Arizona

Utilizing Physician Voices to Define Leadership, Management, and Professionalism in Anesthesiology. *Emily Toutkoushian, The American Board of Anesthesiology; Susan T. Hibbard, The American Board of Anesthesiology; Ni Bei, The American Board of Anesthesiology; Hoda Badr, Thomas Jefferson University; Tianpeng Ye, American Board of Anesthesiology; Youngjun Lee, The American Board of Anesthesiology*

Chair: *Ryan C. Weber, Pepperdine University*

26.065-8. Recent Developments in Multilevel Modeling: Model Estimation and Evaluation (Table 8). SIG-Structural Equation Modeling and Multilevel Modeling Methods; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Slope Difference Testing of Three Way Interactions in Longitudinal Multilevel Models Across Five Statistical Packages. *Peyton Perduyn, University of North Texas; Yan Zhang, University of North Texas; Qi Chen, University of North Texas*

Structural After Measurement Estimation of n-Level Structural Equation Models. *Fangxing Bai, Montana State University; Benjamin Kelcey, University of Cincinnati*

Comparing Pseudo-R-squared Metrics for Multilevel Logistic Regression Models. *Zixie Zheng, University of Washington; Elizabeth A. Sanders, University of Washington*

Chair: *Kejin Lee, Pusan National University*

26.065-9. From Collaboration to Transformation: Evolving Research-Practice Partnerships in Education (Table 9). Division H - Research, Evaluation and Assessment in Schools; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

At Research-Practice Partnership Edges: Expanding Boundaries, Co-Creating Knowledge, and Supporting Racial Equity Joint Work. *Lindsey J. Kaiser, University of Maine; David Goldenkranz, Technology Access Foundation; Amrita Kauldher, Technology Access Foundation; Heather Lechner, Hayward Unified School District; Patricia Woods, Technology Access Foundation*

Boundary Crossing in Hawai'i Education Research Network's (HERN) Tripartite Model. *Carl Francis Moog, University of Hawai'i at Mānoa; Joanna Philippoff, University of Hawai'i at Manoa; Kavita Rao, University of Hawai'i at Mānoa*

Cross-Sector Learning and Organizational Negotiation in an Early Childhood/Ed-Tech Design Research Practice Partnership. *Susan Bush-Mecenas, RAND Corporation; Alice Huguet, RAND Corporation; Sarah Zelazny, RAND Corporation*

From Partnership to Practice: Supporting Mathematics Instructional Improvement Through Adaptive, Equity-Focused RPPs. *Johnna Bolyard, West Virginia University; Courtney Baker, George Mason University; Divya Varier, George Mason University*

Research on the Mechanisms of University-Secondary-Primary School Collaboration in Advancing "High-Quality Future School" Construction. *GAI PINGYUN, East China Normal University; Shuting Sun, East China Normal University; Yuhua Bu, East China Normal University*

Discussant: *William R. Penuel, University of Colorado - Boulder*

26.065-10. Teaching and Learning in Career & Technical Education and Workplace Learning (Table 10). SIG-Career & Technical Education and Workplace Learning; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

From Design to Practice: Integrating Deeper Learning into PBL for School-Based Agricultural Education. *Ying Jin, James Madison University; Chaney W. Mosley, Middle Tennessee State University; Monica B. Smith-Woofter, James Madison University*

How Knowledge Workers Rapidly Learn: Leveraging Situated Contexts, Cognitive Scaffolds, and Networked Learning. *Max Lu, Harvard University; Tessa Forshaw, Harvard University*

Humanizing Hybrid Teams through Organizational Justice: Advancing Work Engagement and Workplace Learning. *Seong Eun Kim, Texas A&M University*

Unpacking Soft Skill Prioritization in Workforce Pathways: A Q Study of Career Center Leaders. *Anthony Mark Gray, Dunwoody College of Technology; Adam K. Atwell, Old Dominion University*

Using Engaged Pedagogy to Incorporate Students' Knowledge to Facilitate Learning in FCS Classrooms. *William Wilton, University of Nebraska - Lincoln*

Chair: *In Heok Lee, University of Georgia*

Discussant: *Matthew S. Giani, University of Texas at Austin*

Division and SIG Posters

26.066. AERA Poster Session Wednesday 3:45pm; Poster Session

26.066-1. Bridging Worlds with Technology in Science Education. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 3:45-5:15pm

Posters:

1. Bridging Perception and Physiology in Elementary Science

Classrooms: Investigating Cognitive Reengagement Using fNIRS and Behavioral Metrics Following Classroom Interruptions (Poster 1). *Richard Lamb, University of Georgia; Caitlin Volante, Vanderbilt University; Viviane Ito, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Lindy Hernandez, Pennsylvania State University; Ashley Anderson, Intuit*

2. Classroom Implementation of an Online Science Modeling Environment that Provides AI-Driven Feedback to Student Drawings (Poster 2). *Natalie Brezack, WestEd; Wynnie Chan, WestEd; Jenna Grady, WestEd; Mingyu Feng, WestEd*
3. Digital Tools as Bridges: A Systematic Review of How K 12 Science Teachers Connect Students' Lives to Disciplinary Science (Poster 3). *Mike Frazier, Michigan State University; Garam A. Lee, Michigan State University; Qiyang Lin, Michigan State University; Jingwen He, University of North Texas; Ryan LeVault, Virginia Commonwealth University; Singith Nuwanga Perera, Virginia Commonwealth University; Christine Lee Bae, Virginia Commonwealth University; Kui Xie, University of Missouri*
4. Exploring the Domain of AI - Driven Applications in Science Education: An Umbrella Review (Poster 4). *Yi Zheng, Hangzhou Normal University; Yumeng Zhu, Zhejiang University; Dan Sun, Hangzhou Normal University*
5. Multimedia's Influence on Children's STEM Experiences: A Bridge from School to Home and Back Again (Poster 5). *Kelly Houle, University of Rhode Island; Sara Sweetman, University of Rhode Island*
6. Technology-enhanced hands-on inquiry in the rural science classroom: Effects on physical knowledge and scientific performance (Poster 6). *Fan Chen, University of Hong Kong; Gaowei Chen, University of Hong Kong*
7. The Effect of Virtual Reality on Chemistry Laboratory Anxiety and Self-Efficacy (Poster 7). *Yanyan Zong, University of Southern California; Rebecca Broyer, University of Southern California; Shalini Ramachandran, Loyola Marymount University; Sheree Fu, California State University - Los Angeles; Steven Cutchin, Boise State University; Erika A. Patall, University of Southern California; Cecilia Zurita Lopez, Chapman University*

26.066-2. Research in Research and Literacy (SIG 11) Poster Session I. SIG-Research in Reading and Literacy; Poster Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 3:45-5:15pm

Posters:

8. Comprehension instruction in five "high-quality" core reading programs (Poster 8). *Peter Dewitz, Mary Baldwin College; Michael Crusco, Virginia Commonwealth University; Savannah Campbell, Scholastic Inc.; Lynn Baker, University of Delaware*
9. Elementary and secondary teachers' disciplinary literacy practice: Comparisons and contrasts (Poster 9). *Patrick*

Burke, Dublin City University

10. Elementary Teachers' Perceptions of Their Literacy Instruction and Curriculum (Poster 10). *Yuzi Gao, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Courtney Hattan, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*
11. Examining Differences in Word-Solving Actions when Reading Decodable and Leveled Text (Poster 11). *Tracy Johnson, University of Indianapolis; Maxiel Abreu-Leon, University of Indianapolis*
12. Geospatial Modeling of Science of Reading Policy Adoption: What matters where? (Poster 12). *Elizabeth Thorne-Wallington, Missouri Western State University*
13. Promoting Reading Accuracy and Fluency Outcomes in Complex Texts for Struggling Readers: A Comparison (Poster 13). *Jake Downs, Utah State University; Kristin Conradi Smith, College of William & Mary; Elfrieda H. Hiebert, TextProject*
14. Resisting the Summer Slide: A Pilot Evaluation of Brilliant Storytellers for Summer Literacy Development (Poster 14). *Sydney Katherine Johnson, Ball State University; Kathrin Maki, University of Florida; Lisa DaVia Rubenstein, Ball State University*
15. The Impact of an Orton-Gillingham-Based Reading Program on Special Education Students' Reading Outcomes (Poster 15). *Norman P. Gibbs, Mesa Unified School District; Margarita Pivovarova, Arizona State University; Jesse Fleming, Arizona State University; Andrew J. Stefanko, University of Wisconsin - Whitewater*
16. Turning the Page: Teachers' Text Selection for Small Group Reading Instruction (Poster 16). *Lisa Cortez Hendricks, Michigan State University; Tanya S. Wright, University of Michigan*
17. Empowering Teacher Efficacy through Structured Professional Development: Advancing Literacy Equity in Low-SES Classrooms (Poster 17). *Joy Watson, University of Louisiana at Lafayette; Amanda S. Mayeaux, University of Louisiana at Lafayette; Tarrah C Davis, University of Louisiana at Lafayette; Latasha Shuford Holt, University of Louisiana at Lafayette*
18. The Development and Validation of a Formative Oral Reading Assessment for The Early Grades (Poster 18). *Emily M. Rodgers, The Ohio State University; Jerome V. D'Agostino, The Ohio State University*

26.066-3. Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis: Methods, Contexts, and Impacts. SIG-Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 3:45-5:15pm

Posters:

19. Boosting Screening Efficiency in Research Synthesis with Text Mining and Machine Learning (Poster 19). *Xiyu Wang, Purdue University; Yukiko Maeda, Purdue University*
20. Enhancing Research Synthesis Efficiency through

Transparent AI-Powered Data Extraction (Poster 20). *Xiyu Wang, Purdue University; Yukiko Maeda, Purdue University; Hua-Hua Chang, Purdue University*

21. Current Landscape of Professional Development of Teachers' Capacity for Computing Education: A Systematic Literature Review (Poster 21). *Xiaoxia A. Newton, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Zhi Li, University of Illinois College of Medicine Rockford; Yi Wang, Purdue University; Beth Auten, University of North Carolina - Charlotte*
22. Enhancing Meta-Analyses with LLM-Assisted Literature Screening: A Case Study on AI-STEM Education and Critical Thinking (Poster 22). *Xuechun Wang, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Alan C. K. Cheung, The Chinese University of Hong Kong*
23. Individual Participant Data Meta-Analysis of Single-Case Experimental Design Data: A Monte Carlo Simulation Study (Poster 23). *Yukang Xue, University at Albany - SUNY; Mariola Moeyaert, University at Albany - SUNY*
24. Knowledge, Equity, and Evolution in Educational Administration Research: A Review of 22,000 Articles (1920-2025) (Poster 24). *Aziz Awaludin, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Saiful Falah, Institut Ummul Quro Al-Islami Bogor*
25. The Hidden Variable: Socioeconomic Status as a Predictor of Standardized Admissions Assessment Performance - A Meta-Analysis (Poster 25). *Kiya Ma, University of Kansas*
26. Designing for Self-Regulation: A Systematic Literature Review of Metacognitive Prompts in Technology-enhanced Learning (Poster 26). *Shiyang Zhang, University of Pennsylvania; Xianghui Meng, Columbia University*

26.066-4. Motivation, Emotion, and Self-Regulation:

Connecting Student Learning and Teacher Practice. SIG-Studying and Self-Regulated Learning; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 3:45-5:15pm

Posters:

27. Academic Burnout in Chinese College Students: Insights into Gender Differences Stress, and Self-Assessment (Poster 27). *Jingyi Tang, Syracuse University; Yibo Cao, Peking University; Minqi Gao, Shanghai Normal University*
28. College Student Adjustment from Pandemic Disruption to Post-COVID Recovery: Exploring Gender Differences, Self-Regulation and Attachment (Poster 28). *Jill D. Salisbury-Glennon, Auburn University; Yan Dai, Tuskegee University; Chih-hsuan Wang, Auburn University*
29. Current Trends in Teacher Knowledge, Beliefs, and Classroom Application of Self-Regulated Learning Strategies (Poster 29). *Stephanie Greenquist-Marlett, Old Dominion University; Linda Bol, Old Dominion University*
30. Examining How Professional Development Affects Teachers' Knowledge, Beliefs, and Practices of Self-Regulated Learning (Poster 30). *Stephanie Greenquist-*

Marlett, Old Dominion University; Claire Consadine, Old Dominion University; Linda Bol, Old Dominion University; Jordan Overton, Old Dominion University; Tian Luo, Old Dominion University

31. Listening to Music Boosts Students' Homework Enjoyment, Focus, and Effort (Poster 31). *Siena Adwere-Boamah, Knox College; Daeun Kim, Knox College; Mai Hasegawa, Knox College; Evan Elijah Morris, Knox College; Sasha Jeffries, Knox College; Jasmine Lerner, Knox College; Aaron Shinefield, Knox College; Leah Binzel, Knox College; Gabriela Orduña-Aparicio, Knox College; Dristi Shrestha, Knox College; Emily Lieder, Eberhard Karls Universität Tübingen*
32. Profiling teachers' self-regulated learning teaching and their relationship with school support and professional well-being (Poster 32). *Renjing Song, Shenzhen No. 12 Kindergarten; Guoguo Chen, Shenzhen No. 12 Kindergarten; Muxuzi Li, Shenzhen No. 12 Kindergarten; Jie Wu, Baicaooyuan kindergarten; Yang Guo, QingXiu kindergarten; Jing Li, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Qiongqiong Wu, Shenzhen No. 10 Kindergarten*
33. Reconceptualizing High-Impact Tutoring Through Self-Regulated Learning Principles: Enhancing Student Learning, Motivation, and Tutor Commitment (Poster 33). *Sahar Wahidi, George Mason University; Anastasia Kitsantas, George Mason University; Roberto A. Pamas, George Mason University; Beth A. Hosek, George Mason University; Haley McKeen, George Mason University; Christine A Nardelli, George Mason University; Katelyn Scott, George Mason University*
34. State-Trait Duality of Self-Efficacy in Mathematical Problem-Posing and Solving: Insights from Chinese Eighth Graders (Poster 34). *QIMENG LIU, Beijing Normal University; Tianxue Cui, Dalian Maritime University; Jian Liu, Beijing Normal University*
35. Uncovering Self-regulated Learning and Metacognitive Processing through Writing (Poster 35). *LaVonda R. Walker, University of Central Florida; Michelle Taub, University of Central Florida; Joel Schneier, University of Central Florida; Sierra Outerbridge, University of Central Florida*

26.066-5. Modeling, Measurement, and Design in Technology-Enhanced Learning Environments. SIG-Technology as an Agent of Change in Teaching and Learning; Poster Session Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 3:45-5:15pm

Posters:

36. Cognitive Diagnostic Modeling from Open Educational Game Data: A Cross-Domain Analysis in Science Learning (Poster 36). *Jewoong Moon, University of Alabama*
37. Characteristics of generated immediate feedback of teachers' improvisational decisions within agentic simulations to support mathematics instruction (Poster 37). *Erin Barno, ETS*

38. Assessing the Validity of Instructional Quality Ratings in a Virtual Reality-Based Teaching Simulation (Poster 38). *Nico Klausner-Thimm, University of Potsdam; Yizhen Huang, University of Potsdam; Eric Richter, KU Eichstätt-Ingolstadt; Dirk Richter, University of Potsdam*
39. Bridging and Reconstructing: Designing a Programming AI Agent to Optimize Learners' Experience and Develop Programming Self-Concept (Poster 39). *Haoming Wang, East China Normal University; Chengliang Wang, Australian Catholic University; Jinhua Shao, Anhui University of Science & Technology; Xianru Shang, Shaanxi University of Science and Technology; Teng Yu, Guangdong Polytechnic Normal University; Yupeng Lin, Tsinghua University*
40. Entropy-Based Analysis of Teacher Adaptability in Generative AI Agents in 3D Teacher Simulations (Poster 40). *Jewoong Moon, University of Alabama; Jieun Lim, Daegu National University of Education; Yunseo Lee, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Gyuri Byun, Seoul National University; Yeil Jeong, Seoul National University; Unggi Lee, Korea University*

26.066-6. Preservice & Practicing Teachers Navigating Digital Spaces. SIG-Media, Culture, and Learning; Poster Session Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 3:45-5:15pm

Posters:

41. Exploring EFL Teachers' Media Literacy in Kazakhstan (Poster 41). *Aigul Beibitkyzy Yeleussiz, Kazakh National Women Teacher Training University*
42. Fostering Digital Citizenship: Preparing Pre-Service Teachers as Agents of Media Literacy (Poster 42). *I-Shin Liu, National Sun Yat-sen University/Institute of Education; Yu-Hui Chang, National Sun Yat-sen University; Yen-Chen Chiang, National Sun Yat-sen University/Institute of Education*
43. Who talks about the future of learning? Examining media discourse of the inevitable GenAI in College teaching and learning (Poster 43). *Yilun Jiang, Michigan State University*
44. Finding Waldo, Missing Reflection: A Case Study in Critical Media Literacy in Teacher Preparation Programs (Poster 44). *Bruno Halpern, Florida Gulf Coast University; Clarisse Halpern, Florida Gulf Coast University; Hasan Aydin, Florida Gulf Coast University*

26.066-7. (Re)Defining and Operationalizing Research Historically and Contemporarily in Urban Spaces. SIG-Urban Learning, Teaching, and Research; Poster Session Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 3:45-5:15pm

Posters:

45. A Literature Review Tracing 60 Years of Research Questions on Black Men and Boys in Urban Education (Poster 45). *Daniel J. Thomas, Texas A&M University;*

Marcus Wayne Johnson, Texas A&M University; John A. Williams, Texas A&M University

46. Celebrating 10 years of JULTR: Living Our Values as Urban Ed Stakeholders [The How is the What] (Poster 46). Jennifer L. Martin, University of Illinois at Springfield; Tabitha Messmore, Kent State University
47. Examining How STEM Interest and Family Support Predict Future STEM Aspirations for Underrepresented Minority Students (Poster 47). Jarrod G. Collins, Texas A&M University; Wisdom Yao Nudze, Texas A&M University; Jose Rosalio Palma, Texas A&M University
48. "No Love and That's What I Fear": Understanding Drill Music as Dialogic Expression for Black Youth (Poster 48). Kelly R. Allen, Augusta University; Ian Levy, Rutgers University; Edmund S. Adjapong, Seton Hall University
49. Systems, Suspensions, and Scores: Predicting Math Performance from Early School Experiences (Poster 49). Micayla Gooden, Texas A&M University; Aminah Crawford, Texas A&M University; Virginia S. Redwine Johnson, Texas A&M University

26.067. Meet the Editors - Journal Talks Session 1. AERA Sessions; Journal Talks
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

1. Theory Into Practice (Table 1). Eric M. Anderman, The Ohio State University; Mollie V. Blackburn, The Ohio State University; Dean S. Cristol, The Ohio State University; Belinda Gimbert, The Ohio State University; Scott L. Graves, The Ohio State University
2. The Urban Review (Table 2). James Martinez, Valdosta State University
3. American Educational Research Journal (Table 3). Motoko Akiba, Florida State University; Alison G. Dover, California State University - Fullerton; Timothy G. Ford, University of Oklahoma; Thomas F. Luschei, Claremont Graduate University; Mariela Aime Rodriguez, University of Texas - San Antonio; Saran Stewart, University of Connecticut; Alexander W. Wiseman, Texas Tech University
4. Journal of Educational and Behavioral Statistics (Table 4). Minjeong Jeon, University of California - Los Angeles; Gongjun Xu, University of Michigan
5. Advancing Women in Leadership Journal (Table 5). Beverly J. Irby, Texas A&M University; Nahed Abdelrahman, The University of Southern Mississippi; Sonia Rodriguez, National University; Julia Nell Ballenger, East Texas A&M University; Jordan Donop, Texas A&M University
6. Beijing International Review of Education (Table 6). Xudong Zhu, Beijing Normal University; Huajun Zhang, Beijing Normal University; Wei Liao, Beijing Normal University
7. Cogent Education (Table 7). Kristen Brida, Taylor & Francis; Josef Buchner, St. Gallen University of Teacher Education; Hengtao Tang, University of South Carolina;

Jason Cong Lin, The Education University of Hong Kong; Kevin Yung, The Education University of Hong Kong

8. Cognition and Instruction (Table 8). Shirin Vossoughi, Northwestern University; Olivia Ortiz, New York University; Jasmine Y. Ma, New York University

9. Contemporary Issues in Technology And Teacher Education (Table 9). Natalie B. Milman, The George Washington University; Chrystalla Mouza, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Marie K. Heath, Loyola University Maryland; Daniel G. Krutka, University of North Texas; Yi Jin, Iowa State University; Ellen B. Meier, Teachers College, Columbia University
10. Early Education and Development (Table 10). Jeffrey Liew, Texas A&M University
11. Educational Evaluation and Policy Analysis (EEPA) (Table 11). Sylvia Hurtado, University of California - Los Angeles; Jade M. Jenkins, University of California - Irvine
12. Educational Researcher - Session 1 (Table 12). Royel M. Johnson, University of Southern California
13. International Studies in Catholic Education (Table 13). John J. Lydon, St. Mary's University Twickenham
14. Journal of Minority Achievement, Creativity & Leadership (Table 14). Fred A. Bonner, Prairie View A&M University
15. Journal of Research on Technology in Education (Table 15). Albert Dieter Ritzhaupt, University of Florida
16. Journal of Montessori Research (Table 16). Angela Murray, University of Kansas
17. Educational Theory (Table 17). Rebecca Taylor, University of Illinois at Chicago
18. The Journal of Null Results and Replications in Education (Table 18). Sarah E. Pennington, Montana State University
19. Journal of General Education (Table 19). Laura Cruz, Pennsylvania State University

26.068. e-Lightning Ed-Talk Session 5 - Stage 1. AERA e-Lightning Ed-Talks; AERA Ed Talk
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Exhibit Hall A - Stage 1; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

- Technology-enhanced hands-on inquiry in the rural science classroom: Effects on physical knowledge and scientific performance (Stage 1, 3:50 PM). Fan Chen, University of Hong Kong; Gaowei Chen, University of Hong Kong
- Digital Tools as Bridges: A Systematic Review of How K 12 Science Teachers Connect Students' Lives to Disciplinary Science (Stage 1, 3:59 PM). Mike Frazier, Michigan State University; Garam A. Lee, Michigan State University; Qiyang Lin, Michigan State University; Jingwen He, University of North Texas; Ryan LeVault, Virginia Commonwealth University; Singith Nuwanga Perera, Virginia Commonwealth University; Christine Lee Bae, Virginia Commonwealth University; Kui Xie, University of Missouri
- Who talks about the future of learning? Examining media

discourse of the inevitable GenAI in College teaching and learning (Stage 1, 4:08 PM). *Yilun Jiang, Michigan State University*

Exploring EFL Teachers' Media Literacy in Kazakhstan (Stage 1, 4:17 PM). *Aigul Beibitkyzy Yeleussiz, Kazakh National Women Teacher Training University*

Examining How Professional Development Affects Teachers' Knowledge, Beliefs, and Practices of Self-Regulated Learning (Stage 1, 4:26 PM). *Stephanie Greenquist-Marlett, Old Dominion University; Claire Consadine, Old Dominion University; Linda Bol, Old Dominion University; Jordan Overton, Old Dominion University; Tian Luo, Old Dominion University*

Listening to Music Boosts Students' Homework Enjoyment, Focus, and Effort (Stage 1, 4:35 PM). *Siena Adwere-Boamah, Knox College; Daeun Kim, Knox College; Mai Hasegawa, Knox College; Evan Elijah Morris, Knox College; Sasha Jeffries, Knox College; Jasmine Lerner, Knox College; Aaron Shinefield, Knox College; Leah Binzel, Knox College; Gabriela Orduña-Aparicio, Knox College; Dristi Shrestha, Knox College; Emily Lieder, Eberhard Karls Universität Tübingen*

Reconceptualizing High-Impact Tutoring Through Self-Regulated Learning Principles: Enhancing Student Learning, Motivation, and Tutor Commitment (Stage 1, 4:44 PM). *Sahar Wahidi, George Mason University; Anastasia Kitsantas, George Mason University; Roberto A. Pamas, George Mason University; Beth A. Hosek, George Mason University; Haley McKeen, George Mason University; Christine A Nardelli, George Mason University; Katelyn Scott, George Mason University*

Chair: *Norma A. Guzman, Texas A&M University - Kingsville*

26.069. e-Lightning Ed-Talk Session 5 - Stage 2. AERA e-Lightning Ed-Talks; AERA Ed Talk
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Exhibit Hall A - Stage 2; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Comprehension instruction in five "high-quality" core reading programs (Stage 2, 3:50 PM). *Peter Dewitz, Mary Baldwin College; Michael Crusco, Virginia Commonwealth University; Savannah Campbell, Scholastic Inc.; Lynn Baker, University of Delaware*

Elementary Teachers' Perceptions of Their Literacy Instruction and Curriculum (Stage 2, 3:59 PM). *Yuzi Gao, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Courtney Hattan, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*

Examining Differences in Word-Solving Actions when Reading Decodable and Leveled Text (Stage 2, 4:08 PM). *Tracy Johnson, University of Indianapolis; Maxiel Abreu-Leon, University of Indianapolis*

Promoting Reading Accuracy and Fluency Outcomes in Complex Texts for Struggling Readers: A Comparison (Stage 2, 4:17 PM). *Jake Downs, Utah State University;*

Kristin Conradi Smith, College of William & Mary; Elfrieda H. Hiebert, TextProject

Resisting the Summer Slide: A Pilot Evaluation of Brilliant Storytellers for Summer Literacy Development (Stage 2, 4:26 PM). *Sydney Katherine Johnson, Ball State University; Kathrin Maki, University of Florida; Lisa DaVia Rubenstein, Ball State University*

Empowering Teacher Efficacy through Structured Professional Development: Advancing Literacy Equity in Low-SES Classrooms (Stage 2, 4:35 PM). *Joy Watson, University of Louisiana at Lafayette; Amanda S. Mayeaux, University of Louisiana at Lafayette; Tarrah C Davis, University of Louisiana at Lafayette; Latasha Shuford Holt, University of Louisiana at Lafayette*

Systems, Suspensions, and Scores: Predicting Math Performance from Early School Experiences (Stage 2, 4:44 PM). *Micayla Gooden, Texas A&M University; Aminah Crawford, Texas A&M University; Virginia S. Redwine Johnson, Texas A&M University*

Celebrating 10 years of JULTR: Living Our Values as Urban Ed Stakeholders [The How is the What] (Stage 2, 4:53 PM). *Jennifer L. Martin, University of Illinois at Springfield; Tabitha Messmore, Kent State University*

Chair: *Theodora Regina Berry, Bloomfield College of Montclair State University*

26.070. e-Lightning Ed-Talk Session 5 - Stage 3. AERA e-Lightning Ed-Talks; AERA Ed Talk
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Exhibit Hall A - Stage 3; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Knowledge, Equity, and Evolution in Educational Administration Research: A Review of 22,000 Articles (1920-2025) (Stage 3, 3:50 PM). *Aziz Awaludin, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Saiful Falah, Institut Ummul Quro Al-Islami Bogor*

Enhancing Research Synthesis Efficiency through Transparent AI-Powered Data Extraction (Stage 3, 3:59 PM). *Xiyu Wang, Purdue University; Yukiko Maeda, Purdue University; Hua-Hua Chang, Purdue University*

Current Landscape of Professional Development of Teachers' Capacity for Computing Education: A Systematic Literature Review (Stage 3, 4:08 PM). *Xiaoxia A. Newton, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Zhi Li, University of Illinois College of Medicine Rockford; Yi Wang, Purdue University; Beth Auten, University of North Carolina - Charlotte*

Boosting Screening Efficiency in Research Synthesis with Text Mining and Machine Learning (Stage 3, 4:17 PM). *Xiyu Wang, Purdue University; Yukiko Maeda, Purdue University*

Assessing the Validity of Instructional Quality Ratings in a Virtual Reality-Based Teaching Simulation (Stage 3, 4:26 PM). *Nico Klausner-Thimm, University of Potsdam; Yizhen Huang, University of Potsdam; Eric Richter, KU Eichstätt-Ingolstadt; Dirk Richter, University of Potsdam*

Wednesday, April 8th, 5:45 pm

AERA Sessions

27.010. 2026 AERA Annual Meeting Opening Plenary Session: Holding Fast to Histories, Holding Fast to Dreams.

AERA Sessions; Invited Speaker Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Concourse Hall; 5:45-7:15pm

Participant:

2026 AERA Land Acknowledgement. *Kelly Leah Stewart, University of California, Los Angeles; Theresa J. Ambo, University of California - Los Angeles*

Chair: *Maisha T. Winn, Stanford University*

Participants: *Daniel Gilbert Solorzano, University of California - Los Angeles; Jarvis R. Givens, Harvard University; Stacey J. Lee, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Veronica Terriquez, University of California - Los Angeles; Amanda R. Tachine, University of Oregon*

Wednesday, April 8th, 7:15 pm

AERA Sessions

28.010. 2026 AERA Annual Meeting Opening Reception.

AERA Sessions; Reception
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Plaza;
7:15-8:15pm

Chairs: *Tabbye M. Chavous, American Educational Research Association; Maisha T. Winn, Stanford University*

Thursday, April 9th, 7:00 am

AERA Related Activities

29.010. AERA Undergraduate Student Workshop - Day 2 (Invitation Only). AERA Related Activities; Workshop
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 505;
7:00am to 7:00pm

Chair: *George L. Wimberly, American Educational Research Association*

Committee Sessions

29.011. AERA Graduate Student Resource Center (Day 2).

Graduate Student Council; Networking Center
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 502B;
7:00am to 10:00pm

Division Sessions

29.012. Division G Rise and Shine Thursday (Division G Members Only). Division G - Social Context of Education; Reception

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
7:00-7:45am

Chair: *Cleveland Hayes, Indiana University - Indianapolis*

29.013. Division I Awards Committee Meeting (Closed Meeting). Division I - Education in the Professions; Board Meeting

Westin Bonaventure, Level 3, Hollywood Ballroom; 7:00-8:00am

Chairs: *Monica M. Cuddy, NBME; Marta van Zanten, FAIMER, A Division of Intealth*

Participants: *EunMi Park, HRDE; Andrew David Bergemann, Baylor College of Medicine; Sarah Schnabel, American Board of Ophthalmology; Patricia S. O'Sullivan, University of California - San Francisco*

29.014. Division K Open House Breakfast. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Reception

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum E;
7:00-7:45am

Thursday, April 9th, 7:45 am

AERA Related Activities

30.010. AERA Fellows Breakfast and Induction Ceremony (Invitation Only). AERA Related Activities; Invited Speaker Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum D; 7:45-9:30am

Committee Sessions

30.011. Sustaining Graduate Research: Funding, Capacity Building, and Professional Growth. Graduate Student Council; Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 402A;
7:45-9:15am

Chair: *Marjorie M. Hahn, Stanford University*

Panelists: *George L. Wimberly, American Educational Research*

Association; Dawn G. Williams, Howard University; Jon Hale, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign

Division Sessions

30.012. Equity Leadership in Challenging Contexts: Recovery, Reform, & Gender Policy Implementation. Division A - Administration; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, La Brea; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Beyond the Risk Status: Understanding Graduation Factors and Experiences of Foster Care Youth. *Victoria Koop, Wichita State University; Whitney Crager, Wichita State University; Wanda Parker-Givens, Wichita State University; Vernetta Hill, Wichita State University; Remington Putter, Wichita State University*

Learning from Successful COVID-19 Academic Recovery: Policies, Practices, and Equity-Oriented Beliefs of District Leaders. *Britney L. Jones, Fairfield University; Shannon Holder, Central Connecticut State University*

Making Gender Policies Your Own: A Comparative Case Study of NYC Schools' Gender Guidelines Appropriation. *Carolina Snaider, University of Texas at Austin; Mauro Moschetti, Autonomous University of Barcelona*

Using "Beating the Odds" Methodology to Help Identify Equity-Focused Urban School Leaders. *Samuel P. Whalen, University of Illinois at Chicago*

Chair: *Matthew S. McCluskey, University of Vermont*

Discussant: *Jeff Walls, University of Iowa*

30.013. Global Citizenship in Motion: Critical Pedagogies of Race, History, and Decolonization. Division B - Curriculum Studies; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304A; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

The Development of Identities in Hong Kong: Global-National Citizenship Education in Secondary Curricula, 1985–2024. *Isabelle Rose Coloma, Stanford University; Xiangqian Yu, Stanford University*

Decolonizing Education in Kenya: Examining Colonial Legacies and Reintegrating Indigenous Knowledge and Languages into the School Curriculum. *Jane Jebet Bitok, Kenyatta University*

Film as (Black) Curriculum: Learning Slavery and Race Through Black American History Crash Course Films. *Keffrelyn D. Brown, University of Texas at Austin; Anthony L. Brown, University of Texas at Austin; Nkasano R. Fullerton, University of Texas at Austin*

"Study Rather than Believe": Septima P. Clark's Civic Education Lessons for Social Studies Education. *Kristen Duncan, Clemson University; Tiffany O. Harris, College of Charleston; ArCasia D. James-Galloway, Texas A&M*

University

Chair: *Tanya R. Manning-Lewis, Thompson Rivers University*

Discussant: *Danielle Charlemagne, University of Georgia*

30.014. Circling Back and Moving Forwards in Digital Literacies Research. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Structured Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 515A; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

1. Toward an Ecosystemic Understanding of Digital Literacy (Poster 1). *Maria Cristina Martinez-Bravo, A. T. Still University; Charo Sádaba-Chalezquer, A. T. Still University; Javier Serrano-Puche, University of Navarra*
2. Home Literacy Environment and the Development of Critical Reading Skills in the Digital Era (Poster 2). *Minna Torppa, University of Jyväskylä; Jenni Ruotsalainen, University of Jyväskylä; Mari Manu, University Of Jyväskylä; Maria Maria Psyridou, Jyväskylä University; Jenni Salminen, Jyväskylä University; Panayiota Kendeou, University of Minnesota; Leena Paakkari, Jyväskylä University*
3. Children's Digital Literacy: Interdisciplinary insights for Informed, Productive, and Safe Practices (Poster 3). *Lisa K Kervin, University of Wollongong; Jessica Mantei, University of Wollongong; Cathrine Neilsen-Hewett, University of Wollongong; Dylan Cliff, University of Wollongong; Rebecca Ng, Australian Research Council Centre of Excellence for the Digital Child, University of Wollongong*
4. Within and Outside the Frame: The Nuances of Meaning Making in Digital Environments from the Web Browser to the Metaverse (Poster 4). *Brady L. Nash, University of Florida; Csaba Osvath, University of South Florida*
5. Anti-Racist Practices and Pedagogies for and Within Digital Spaces (Poster 5). *Ian O'Byrne, College of Charleston; Shelbie Witte, University of North Dakota; Bryan R. Crandall, Fairfield University; Christian Z. Goering, University of Arkansas; Jennifer Dail, Kennesaw State University; Detra Price-Dennis, The Ohio State University; Raúl Alberto Mora, Universidad Pontificia Bolivariana*
6. Digital Literacies for Disciplinary Learning: Theoretical Convergences and Methodological Expansions (Poster 6). *Michael Manderino, Northern Illinois University; Jill M. Castek, University of Arizona*
7. Designing Digitally Supported Inquiry-Based Pedagogies to Cultivate Multiple Literacies, Critical Thinking, Disciplinary Learning, and Participatory Action (Poster 7). *Julie Coiro, University of Rhode Island; Carita Kiili, Tampere University; Jon M. Wargo, University of Michigan; Beth R. Holland, FullScale*
8. Digital Game Literacies (Poster 8). *Alex Bacalja, The University of Melbourne; Sandra Schamroth Abrams, University of South Africa*
9. Positioning Theory as an Expansive Lens for Research on

- Digital Literacies (Poster 9). *Mary B. McVee, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Zhiyi Liu, University at Buffalo - SUNY*
10. Theorizing everyday digital literacies for adult learners (Poster 10). *Suzanne K. Smythe, Simon Fraser University; Jenifer Vanek, World Education*
11. Second-Order Discourse Synthesis: How Learners Comprehend and Reconstruct Information from Digital, Multimodal Texts (Poster 11). *Leah Burger, University of South Florida; Jennifer Schneider, Oklahoma State University; James R. King, University of South Florida*
12. Designing Personalized Socioculturally Responsive Assessments of Digital Literacies (Poster 12). *Jesse R. Sparks, Educational Testing Service; Zuowei Wang, Educational Testing Service; Tenaha P. O'Reilly, Educational Testing Service; Eowyn P. O'Dwyer, Rutgers University*
- Chairs: *Jill M. Castek, University of Arizona; Julie Coiro, University of Rhode Island; Jesse R. Sparks, Educational Testing Service; Carita Kiili, Tampere University; Elena Forzani, Boston University*
- Discussant: *Patricia A. Alexander, University of Maryland*

30.015. Reimagining Epistemic Cognition for a Changing World: Knowing in an Age of Too Much Information. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Symposium Westin Bonaventure, Level 3, Avalon; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

- Rational Thinking and Argument Evaluation in Higher Education Students. *Johanna Grimm, University of Würzburg; Tobias Richter, University of Würzburg*
- Race-Reimagining Epistemic Cognition: Centering Marginalized Voices during Online Learning. *Krista R. Muis, McGill University; Nikki G. Lobczowski, McGill University; Chelsea Kisil, McGill University; Martina Calçada Kohatsu, McGill University; Stephanie Bowen, McGill University; Shuting Wang, McGill University; Shasha Li, McGill University; Romane Monnet, McGill University; LUYAO XU, McGill University; Mengqian Wu, McGill University; Paul A. Schutz, University of Arizona*
- Emotion-Driven Belief Updating: How Feelings Shape Evidence Evaluation Across Political and Non-Political Topics. *Gabe Avakian Orona, Boston College*
- How Advanced Students Self-Regulate their Higher-Order Thinking in Three Disciplines. *Jeff A. Greene, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Aditi Ahuja, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Yeojin Choi, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Ruogu Xu, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*
- Chair: *Gabe Avakian Orona, Boston College*
- Discussant: *Gale M. Sinatra, University of Southern California*

30.016. Everything Ain't for Everybody: Refusal as a Methodological Practice of Purposeful Data Disclosure. Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies;

Symposium
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 7th Floor,
Hollywood Ballroom I; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

- Crossing Data Disclosure Thresholds: Navigating Access, Trust, and Invitation. *Marcus Wayne Johnson, Texas A&M University; LaShawn Faith Washington, University of Texas at Austin*
- Revealing with Intention, Concealing with Care: Data Disclosure as a Relational Method. *Julissa O. Muñoz, University of California - Los Angeles; Jasmin Patron-Vargas, Texas A&M University; Pablo Montes, Texas Christian University*
- Exposure Without Shelter: When Visibility Becomes Vulnerability in Data Disclosure. *Devin Walker, Cabrillo College*

Chair: *Cynthia S. Salinas, University of Texas at Austin*
Discussant: *Luis Urrieta, University of Texas at Austin*

30.017. Truth-Telling and Transformation: Critical, Reparative, and Community-Engaged Historical Methods Across Educational Contexts. Division F - Historical Inquiry in Education; Symposium Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 303A; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

- Campus Disorientation Tours as Critical Historical Practice. *Tonya Kneff-Chang, University of Michigan*
- Roots of Resistance: Land, Memory, and Emotional Geographies in Ethnic Studies Pedagogy. *Mariana E. Ramirez, University of California - Irvine; Roxana Daylen Dueñas, Los Angeles Unified School District*
- "This Work is Care Work": Filipina/x/o American Community Museums and Historical Reparative Work. *Paulina Fraser, University of Michigan*
- RHI - Reparative Historical Inquiry. *Aimee Medeiros, University of California - San Francisco; Jason Glenn, University of Kansas Medical Center; Norlissa Cooper, University of California - San Francisco*
- Detroit Public School History Museum: Participatory Archiving, Design-Infused History Practices, Cross-Cultural History. *Dannah Elise Wilson, Detroit Public School History Museum; Mehzabin Kaboo, Wayne State University*
- Chair: *Kimberly C. Ransom, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*
- Discussant: *David G. García, University of California - Los Angeles*

30.018. Fugitive Spaces and Geographies of Spatial Justice throughout Social Contexts of Education. Division G - Social Context of Education; Paper Session Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 301A; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Spatial Exclusion as Discipline: Anti-Black Spatial Imaginaries and the Racialized Control of Black Students. *DeMarcus A Jenkins, University of Pennsylvania; Ayana Cheyenne Colvin, University of Pennsylvania; Samantha Bello, University of Pennsylvania*

Fugitive Spaces in Practice: Student Voice to Disrupting Anti-Blackness. *Rema E. Reynolds Vassar, Wayne State University; Donya Odum, Eastern Michigan University*

Schools as a Borderland: Navigating Citizenship, Surveillance, and Ideological Violence. *Tracie Trinidad, Aurora Public Schools; Paulina Lerma, Denver Public Schools*

Educational Geographies: Post-Brown v. Board Conjunctural Analysis. *Dennis Williams, University of Virginia*

Maroon Geographies: A Black Methodological Framework Rooted in Fugitive Epistemology. *MeYa Elizabeth Hargett, Pepperdine University*

Chair: *Shawn S. Savage, University of North Carolina - Wilmington*

Discussant: *Mariaelois Carambo, Drexel University*

30.019. Advancing Professional Competency and Learning.

Division I - Education in the Professions; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 8;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

A National Survey of Anesthesiology Residency Programs' Milestones Implementation. *Ni Bei, The American Board of Anesthesiology; Emily Toutkoushian, The American Board of Anesthesiology; Huaping Sun, The American Board of Anesthesiology; Ann Elizabeth Harman, American Board of Anesthesiology*

From Cases to Constructs: What Real-World Clinical Reasoning Reveals About Gaps in Medical Assessment. *Kelly Edwards, American Board of Pediatrics*

Improving Medical Students' Communication Skills Through Feedback: Evidence from the Communication Learning Assessment. *Anastasiya A. Lipnevich, City University of New York; Angelo D'Addario, National Board of Medical Examiners; Thea Musselman, National Board of Medical Examiners; Krista D. Mattern, National Board of Medical Examiners*

Professional Competencies for Human-AI Collaboration : A Delphi Study on HRD Practitioners in the Era of AI Transformation. *Boyoung Kim, Korea Univeristy; Gyeong Mi Heo, Korea University*

Chair: *Damian M. Berry, Baylor College of Medicine*

Discussant: *Maura Polansky, University of Illinois at Chicago*

30.020. Educating for Equity and Excellence: Perspectives on Motivation, Cultural Responsiveness, and Professionalism.

Division I - Education in the Professions;
Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Atrium III;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Applying the Servingness Framework to Improve Outcomes of Diverse Students in Medical Schools. *Katherine Arias Garcia, University of California - Irvine; Nicole Perez, University of Illinois at Chicago*

Exploring Motivational Predictors of Engineering Students' Intention to Teach. *Nathaniel Hunsu, University of Georgia; Olanrewaju Paul Olaogun, Merrimack College*

Fieldwork Preceptors' Perspectives on Professionalism in Occupational Therapy. *Mary Roduta Roberts, University of Alberta; Delaina Coupal, University of Alberta; Anastasia Khorikova, University of Alberta; Kiana Mann, University of Alberta; Rene Russo, University of Alberta*

Scaffolding Culturally Responsive Practice Through the Science of Learning and Cultural Humility. *Jamie B. Martin, University of Missouri - St. Louis; Tabari Asim Coleman, University of Missouri - St. Louis; Toni Harris, East St. Louis School District #189; Crystal Isom, Casa Esperanza Montessori School; Jennifer Niebrzydowski, Special School District*

Chair: *Lynn Foster-Johnson, Dartmouth College*

Discussant: *Leila Amiri, University of Vermont*

30.021. Meeting the Moment: A Panel on Researching the Impact of Anti-DEI Action in Higher Education (Division J Vice Presidential Session).

Division J - Postsecondary Education; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum H;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Political Polarization and Institutional Betrayal A Narrative Analysis of Diversity Professionals and Anti-DEI Attacks. *Kaleb L. Briscoe, University of Oklahoma*

On the Grounds: Campus Staff Efforts Amidst Anti-DEI Pressures. *Katherine S. Cho, Loyola University Chicago*

Navigating Anti-CRT Legislation: Black Chief Diversity Officers' Experiences in Higher Education. *O'Juan D. Edwards, Florida A&M University*

Liminality in Compliance: Organizational Responses To Anti-DEI Policy in Higher Education. *Daniela Juarez, University of Chicago*

Chair: *Jeffrey K. Grim, George Mason University*

Discussant: *Jeffrey K. Grim, George Mason University*

30.022. Rethinking equity in higher education.

Division J - Postsecondary Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum G;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Low-Income College Students' Academic Success: Exploring the Role of Spatial Differences in Precollege Communities. *N Tennessee, University of Iowa; Joseph Kitchen, University of Southern California; Zoë Corwin, University of Southern California; Nicholas A. Bowman, University of Iowa*

Navigating Disability Disclosure in College: A Mixed-Methods Exploration of Peer, Faculty, and Staff Contexts. *Ryan A. Mata, University of Minnesota; Stephanie W. Cawthon, University of Texas at Austin; Desirée Lama, University of Texas at Austin*

Navigating Intersecting Identities: A Portrait of Muslim Female Immigrant Students' Identity Development in Higher Education. *Shaimaa Ibrahim, William & Mary*

Out and Overseas: Rethinking LGBT Student Mental Health Through a Global Lens (2017–2024). *Feifan Ma, The Ohio State University; Allen Mallory, The Ohio State University*

Shifting Perceptions of the Value of Higher Education Among Low-Income Students at a Selective University. *Annie Carlson Welch, University of Georgia; Amy Elizabeth Stich, University of Georgia*

Discussant: *Prilly Bicknell-Hersco, York University*

30.023. Toward effective and equitable career-based learning: Multidisciplinary perspectives on the college-to-career transition. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum F; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Diverse Models of Work-Based Learning: Strengthening Higher Education's Career Value. *Nichole Torpey-Saboe*
From College to Career: How Co-ops Shape Initial Labor Market Transitions. *Enrique Eduardo Valencia Lopez, University of California - Berkeley; Oded Mcdossi, Tel Aviv University; Faith Ann Couts, University of California - Irvine; Richard B. Arum, University of California - Irvine*
Rethinking STEM Career Guidance: Do Integrative Career Fit Assessments Lead to More Women in STEM? *Layla Dang, Michigan State University; Kevin Hoff, Michigan State University; Tara Behrend, Michigan State University*

How Organizational Contexts Contribute to Career Crystallization: The Case of Latine STEM Students at HSIs. *Lauren M. Shook, University of Texas - El Paso; Edwin J. Perez, University of Texas - El Paso; Anne-Marie Nunez, University of Texas - El Paso*

Chair: *Anne-Marie Nunez, University of Texas - El Paso*

Discussant: *Adrianna Kezar, University of Southern California*

30.024. Teacher Educators of Color Under Attack. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 6; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Inside and Against: Abolitionist Educators as Mitigators, Refusers, and Protectors. *Estefania Rodriguez Sanchez, Stanford University*

Restoring a Teacher Educator: Endarkened Feminism. *Chanelle Wilson, Bryn Mawr College*

Stories of Resistance: Poetic Insights from BIPOC Women

Teacher Educators Confronting Anti-DEI Legislation in Florida. *Elyse Hambacher, University of Florida; Jalea Turner, University of Florida; Emilie Mitescu Reagan, Claremont Graduate University*

Teacher Educators of Color Navigating the Resurgence of White Supremacy in Education. *Amos Joon Lee, University of California - Riverside; Sharon Leathers, Ramapo College; Ranita Cheruvu, University of North Texas; Ramon Vasquez, University of Minnesota*

Chair: *Darolyn A. Flaggs, Kennesaw State University*

Discussant: *Saili S. Kulkarni, San Jose State University*

30.025. Classrooms Under Fire: Teacher Well-Being, Student Belonging, and the Politics of Schooling. Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 10; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Why Are They Not Here: Student, Teacher, & Administrator Perspectives on Absenteeism/Tardiness in Baltimore City. *Richard Lofton, Johns Hopkins University; Yutong Xie, Johns Hopkins University; Joshua Childs, University of Texas at Austin*

Refusal & Discipline: Racialized Schooling in East Texas. *Cecelia Jordan, University of Texas at Austin*

The Impact of Anti-CRT Laws and Rhetoric on Teacher Well-Being. *Michaela Perneti, University of Texas at Austin; Danielle Sutherland, Towson University; Emily Germain, Learning Policy Institute*

Connecting the Dots: Patterns and Mechanisms of Parent-Child Engagement in Texts4Teens. *Brian Holzman, Texas A&M University; Oralia Zamarripa, Texas A&M University; Shuyu Wang, Texas A&M University; Jinhua Zhao, Texas A&M University; Susanna Loeb, Stanford University; Kalena Cortes, Texas A&M University*

Chair: *Sheila R. Vaidya, Drexel University*

Discussant: *Linn E. Posey-Maddox, Temple University*

30.026. Money Talks: Implementing and Interpreting Values Through Education Finance Policy. Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 1; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Change and Disparity in College Athletics Finance in the NIL Era. *Albert Loera, University of Nevada, Las Vegas*

District Implementation of English Learner Funding Policy: Evidence from Michigan. *Caroline Bartlett, University of Tennessee; David Klayton, Michigan State University; Ajay Srikanth, American Institutes for Research*

Exploring the Implementation of the California Community Schools Partnership Program Through LEA Expenditure. *Andres Fernandez-Vergara, University of California - Los Angeles; Dandan Yang, University of California - Los Angeles*

Angeles; Marisa Saunders, University of California - Los Angeles

Signal or Static? Unpacking ESSER Expenditures with Benford's Law. Jason Godfrey, Harvard University
Unearthing the Ecological Impacts of Workforce Compensation Disparities. Maria Mavrides Calderon, Hunter College - CUNY

Chair: Miyoshi Juergensen, University of Alabama - Birmingham
Discussant: Kendall Dwayne Deas, University of South Carolina

30.027. The Special Education Teacher Workforce: New Evidence on Composition, Distribution, and Effectiveness Across Contexts. Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 2; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

The Composition, Distribution, and Stability of the Special Education Teacher Workforce in Seven States. Allison F. Gilmour, American Institutes for Research; Brendan Bartanen, University of Virginia; Elizabeth A. Bettini, Boston University; Li Feng, Texas State University; Jamie Klinenberg, American Institutes for Research; Loretta Mason-Williams, Binghamton University - SUNY; Christopher Redding, University of Florida; LaRon A. Scott, University of Virginia; Roddy Theobald, American Institutes for Research

Emergency Teacher Certifications in Special Education: Implications for Educators and Their Students. Tashnuva Shaheen, Boston University; Hannah Kistler, Brown University

Comparing Special Education Teachers in Public and Private Schools Using Administrative Data. Nicholas James Ainsworth, University of California - Irvine; Aaron J. Ainsworth, University of California - Irvine

"Bringing My 'A Game'": Exploring the Situated Nature of Special Education Teacher Effectiveness. Hannah Morris Mathews, University of Florida; Elizabeth Grobart, University of Wisconsin - Parkside; Jennifer Curran, University of Florida; Gabriella Arfaras, University of Florida

Chair: Nicholas James Ainsworth, University of California - Irvine
Discussants: Emily K. Penner, University of California - Irvine; Christopher Cleveland, Brown University

SIG Sessions

30.028. How Students Engage with GenAI: From Resistance to Empowerment. SIG-Advanced Technologies for Learning; Paper Session

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Beaudry A; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Neurodivergent Students' Perceptions of AI: Impact on

Autonomy, Competence and Relatedness in Higher Education. Jeanette Villanueva Padilla, University of Southern California

Can Prompting Be Taught? Enhancing AI Literacy Among Higher Education Students. Stefanie Zarnow, Ludwig Maximilian University of Munich; Lisa Anna Matuschek, Ludwig Maximilian University of Munich

Feeling the Future: Indonesian Students' Sentiments Toward Generative Artificial Intelligence for Learning. Aziz Awaludin, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Ibrahim -, Monash University; Ahmad Ardillah Rahman, University College London - IOE

Students Dissecting, Mimicking, and Resisting Generative AI for Civic and Humanistic Purposes. Daniel P. Moore, Seton Hall University; Antero Garcia, Stanford University; Nicole Mirra, University of California - Los Angeles; Matthew Berland, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Max Shafer-Landau, University of Wisconsin - Madison

What Affect Future Use Intention? Unpacking Engineering Students' Perceptions Toward Generative AI in Learning. Daihan Xu, University College London; Matheus de Andrade, University College London - IOE; Diana Martin, University College London

Discussant: Xinxin Feng, University of Washington

30.029. Archival Pedagogy: Moving Images as Research, Resistance, and Relational Learning. SIG-Arts-Based Educational Research; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304B; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Attuning to Presentimiento: Creating Visual Testimonios through Embodied Analysis in an Ethnic Studies Classroom. Wendy Barrales, John Jay College, City University of New York (CUNY)

Counter-Archives of the Doctoral Journey: Junk Journaling as Archive-Building in Motion. Bianca Gonzalez, McGill University

Archival Engagement as Educational Infrastructure: Digitizing Guatemalan Film Collections as an Act of Pedagogical Possibility. Alex Mejía, San Francisco State University

Chair: Bianca Gonzalez, McGill University

Discussant: Jennifer Florencio, Claremont University - Claremont McKenna College

30.030. Interrogating Access to Bilingual Programs for Multilingual Learners with Disabilities. SIG-Bilingual Education Research; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 301B; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Bilingual Education Enrollment for Multilingual English Learner-Classified Students with Disabilities: Evidence from Oregon. Karen D. Thompson, Oregon State University;

Katherine Bromley, University of Oregon; Ilana M. Umansky, University of Oregon; Nami Shin, University of Kansas

Ableism, Gentrification, and the Exclusion of Multilingual Learners with Disabilities from Bilingual Education Programs. *Kate Menken, Queens College; Ivana Espinet, Kingsborough Community College - CUNY; Maria Cioe-Pena, University of Pennsylvania; Maria Teresa Sanchez Stakeholder Insights and Narratives at the Intersection of Dual Language Bilingual Education and Special Education.*

Briseida E. Tijerina M. Cardoza, University of Texas - San Antonio; Kathryn I. Henderson, University of Texas - San Antonio; Zhongfeng Tian, Rutgers University - Newark; Carly C. Leech, The University of Texas at San Antonio

Chairs: *Sara E.N. Kangas, Lehigh University; Rosalia Pacheco, University of New Mexico; Sunaina Shenoy, University of New Mexico*

Discussant: *Deborah K. Palmer, University of Colorado - Boulder*

30.031. Exploring Formative Assessment Practices and Policies in Latin American and European Countries: A Cross-national Comparative Overview. SIG-Classroom Assessment Cosponsored with Division H - Research, Evaluation and Assessment in Schools; Symposium InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Echo Park; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Formative Assessment in Brazil: Teachers' Perceptions, Practices, and Challenges. *Paulo Sérgio Garcia, Universidade de São Caetano do Sul (USCS)*

From Feedback to Autonomy: Exploring the Relationship Between Formative Assessment and Self-Regulation in Mathematics Learning Among Portuguese Students. *Vera Monteiro, ISPA-Instituto Universitário*

Chilean Pre-Service Teachers Approaches to Classroom Assessment. *Valeria Carolina Zunino-Edelsberg, University of California - Davis; Megan E. Welsh, University of California - Davis; Maria Veronica Santelices, Catholic University of Chile*

Preparing Formative Assessment Literate Teachers: A Blurry Snapshot from Italy. *Serafina Pastore, University of Bari*

Chairs: *Serafina Pastore, University of Bari; Paulo Sérgio Garcia, Universidade de São Caetano do Sul (USCS)*

Discussant: *Dustin Sonny James Van Orman, Western Washington University*

30.032. White Epistemic and Affective Violence: From Gaslighting to Innocence. SIG-Critical Examination of Race, Ethnicity, Class and Gender in Education; Paper Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Plaza I; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Emotions and Whiteness: Discourses on the Purpose of Higher

Education. *Antonia Bacigalupa Albaum, Indiana University; Angie L. Miller, Indiana University*

Toward A Racial Microaggressions Model Analysis of White Innocence. *Richard A. Orozco, University of Arizona*
Understanding Racist Gaslighting Tactics: Disinformation, Decontextualization, and Demagoguery in Attacks on CRT. *Rican Vue, University of California - Riverside; Katria Txay Ly, University of California - Riverside*

Dear Karen: Get Your Stiletto Off My Neck! Examining Racialized Allyship and the Sisterhood Myth. *Leah P. Hollis, Pennsylvania State University*

"We Belong Everywhere": Disrupting White Parental Authority Through the Counter-Narrative of a Black Male Educator. *Stuart Rhoden, Arizona State University*

Chair: *Jazmin Pichardo, University of Maryland*

Discussant: *Carlton E. Green, University of Maryland*

30.033. Early Childhood Policy across States. SIG-Early Education and Child Development; Paper Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Georgia I; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Policy Ambiguity and Preschool Inclusion. *Karin Garver, Rutgers University*

State Policies and Community Characteristics: Key Factors in Infant and Toddler Enrollment Patterns. *Gerilyn Slicker, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Alison Hooper, University of Alabama; Joon-Ho Lee, University of Alabama; Amanda Zapata, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Chelsie Shurtleff, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Leticia Delgado, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*

Examining the Relationship Between Care Quality and Stability Among Children Using Child Care Subsidies. *Yilin Wang, Boston College; Yoonsook Ha, Boston University; Juliann Nicholson, Boston University; Briana Le, Boston University*

Mirrors and Mechanisms of Power: Nine States-Based Kindergarten Social Studies Standards. *Sara Michael-Luna, University of Central Florida*

Chair: *Sara Michael-Luna, University of Central Florida*

Discussant: *Noel E. Kelly, Oakland University*

30.034. Revolutionizing Education, Revitalized: The Rise of Creative Resistance in Youth Participatory Action Research. SIG-Grassroots Community and Youth Organizing for Educational Justice; Symposium JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 7; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

"Don't Drink the Water!": Desert Stories of Environmental Justice, YPAR in an Afterschool club. *Julio Cammarota, University of Arizona*

Fostering Joy And Liberation: The Healing Path of Youth Participatory Action Research. *Jennifer Ayala, Saint Peter's University*

How Are We Gonna Turn This Into Music? We're Not. We Are Here To Explore; Making Meaning And a Music of the Oppressed. *Martin Urbach, Graduate Center - CUNY; Madeline Fox, Brooklyn College*

Facilitating Space for Creative Resistance through Literacy and Arts-Based Methods. *Courtney Mauldin-Jones, Syracuse University*

Chair: *Ashley D. Dominguez, University of Arizona*

Discussant: *Julio Cammarota, University of Arizona*

30.035. International Studies SIG Structure Poster Session.

SIG-International Studies; Structured Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 515B;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

1. Strategic Marketing to International Students: How China's Leading AI Universities Position Themselves Globally (Poster 1). *Dong Chen, University of Arizona; Gary D. Rhoades, University of Arizona*
2. The Perceived Affordability of Foreign-Related Higher Education Programs (FREPs) in Vietnam (Poster 2). *Loan Thi Phuong Le, Van Lang University; Minh Huynh, University of Michigan; Binh Chi Bui, The University of Texas at El Paso*
3. The (Trans)formation of Scholarly Selves in International Higher Education: A Collaborative Autoethnography (Poster 3). *Peng Yin, University of California - Berkeley; Yuriko Sato, University of Wisconsin-Madison; Sarang Kim, University of Oklahoma; Marisa Lally, Georgia Southern University*
4. Transforming BRICS Education Policy in International Countries (Poster 4). *Michele Schmidt, Simon Fraser University*
5. Unseen Struggles, Global Aspirations: Centering the Experience of International Graduate Students in the U.S. (Poster 5). *Malachi Okechi Chukwu, Washington State University; Amir Asim Gilmore, Washington State University*
6. Validating a Faculty Governance Perception Scale in Kuwait's Higher Education Context (Poster 6). *ABDULRAHMAN ALAJMI, Kuwait University; Courtney Stone, Arizona State University; Audrey Amrein-Beardsley, Arizona State University*
7. Voices From the Classroom: Shaping English Language Conferences in Jordan (Poster 7). *James Badger, University of North Georgia; Susan L. Ogletree, Georgia State University; Juman Al Bukhari, University of North Georgia*
8. We're still here: (Im)mobilities in film for the American university (Poster 8). *Oliver R Keels, Colorado State University - Pueblo*
9. What Matters Most? A Meta-Analysis of Factors Associated with International Students' Cross-cultural Adaptation in China (Poster 9). *Siyuan Wang, Renmin University of China; Weichen Zhang, Renmin University of China; Xiang HU, Renmin University of China; Li Lei, Renmin University of*

China

10. Women and reciprocity in the international school sector: A case study of hope in a South Asian context (Poster 10). *Nicola Sum, Monash University*

Chair: *Victoria Showunmi, University College London - IOE*

30.036. Reclaiming Memory, Rendering Futures: VR Chicana and Latina Testimonios and Archival Justice in Stockton, CA. SIG-Latina/o/x Research Issues; Symposium JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Plaza II; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

- Embodied Resistance: Testimonio, Archival Research, and Chicana Feminist Futuring. *Nancy Huante-Tzintzun, California State University - Sacramento*
- Testimonio Research as Transformative Student Praxis. *Glenda Vargas, California State University - Sacramento; Gustavo Rodriguez Roa, California State University - Sacramento*
- Designing Justice: Producing VR Testimonios for Public Engagement. *Diego Bonilla, California State University - Sacramento; Miguel Ortiz Ulloa, California State University - Sacramento*
- Curating Public Memory: VR Testimonios as Collective Healing and Political Pedagogy. *Vanessa Maldonado Soto, California State University - Sacramento; Silvia Soto, California State University - Sacramento; Sebastian Perez, California State University - Sacramento; Nancy Huante-Tzintzun, California State University - Sacramento*

Chair: *Ricky Gutierrez-Maldonado, Cosumnes River College*

Discussant: *Sylvia Mendoza, University of Texas - San Antonio*

30.037. STEM Education Across K-12 Contexts. SIG-Learning Sciences; Paper Session Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Los Cerritos; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

- Mapping the affective trajectories of young people into science. *Emily MacLeod, McGill University; Jrene Rahm, University of Montréal*
- Computational Thinking and Participation in Rural Ag STEM: A Comparative Case Study of Two Middle School Teams. *Selcuk Kilinc, Texas A&M University; Tugce Aldemir, Texas A&M University; Vivek Sabanwar, Texas A&M University; Ali Bicer, Texas A&M University; Donggil Song, Texas A&M University*
- When Students Disagree About What Counts as Science: Examining Deep Epistemic Disagreements in Science Classrooms. *Noora Fatima Noushad, University of Pennsylvania; Susan A. Yoon, University of Pennsylvania; Clark A. Chinn, Rutgers University; Claire LeBovidge, University of Pennsylvania; Huma Hussain-Abidi, Rutgers University*
- Not Enough Math to Play With: Constructing Playworlds in K-12 Schools. *Jamie Vescio, Vanderbilt University; Jingyi*

Chen, Vanderbilt University; Karen Underwood, Vanderbilt University; Candice Love, University of Maryland
Spatial Ability and Epistemic Actions in Digital Tangram Puzzles. *Kelsey E. Schenck, Southern Methodist University; Prajakt Pande, Southern Methodist University*

30.038. Teachers at the Center: Reimagining Education Through Voice and Vision. SIG-Lives of Teachers; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Georgia II; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

(Re)imagining the Futures of Teaching and Teacher Education: Whose Voice is Heard? *Maria A. Flores, University of Minho*

Echoes of Presence: Teachers' Voices as Embodied Practice in Everyday Professional Life. *Qinwei Qi, East China Normal University*

Imagining Beyond the Margins: Muslim Teachers and the Work of Liberation. *Mayida Zaal, Montclair State University; Nushrat Hoque, Florida International University; Chedia Ayari, Montclair State University; Maheen Ahmad, Montclair State University; Amir Billups; Manar Hussein, Montclair State University; Nagla Bedir, Perth Amboy Public Schools*

What Matters to Teachers: Alignment with Contemporary Educational Research. *David T. Marshall, Auburn University; Andrew Pendola, Auburn University; Tim Pressley, Christopher Newport University*

Chair: *Melanie Muskin, Northwestern University*

30.039. Reimagining Professional Learning Structures: Supporting Teacher Educators to Lead Ambitious and Equitable Mathematics Teacher Learning. SIG-Research in Mathematics Education; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum A; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Pedagogies of Practice for Responsive Facilitation: Combining and Unpacking Representations and Approximations. *Gil Schwartz, Weizmann Institute of Science; Michael Jarry-Shore, North Carolina State University; Hilda Borko, Stanford University*

Learning to Facilitate Productive Lesson Debriefs Through Meta-Coaching. *Michael Jarry-Shore, North Carolina State University; Hilda Borko, Stanford University; Meghan Smith Durkin, Stanford University; Marsha M. Ing, University of California - Riverside; Thomas M. Smith, University of California - Davis*

Coaching Professional Learning Structures that Facilitate Coaches' Relational Practices. *Rebekah Elliott, Oregon State University; Melinda Knapp, Oregon State University - Cascades*

Structuring Deep and Specific Conversations: The Work of

Facilitators of Mathematics Teacher Professional Learning. *Kelly A. McKie, University of Delaware; Lynsey K. Gibbons, University of Delaware; James Hiebert, University of Delaware*

Responding to Emergent Problems of Practice in Side-by-side Coaching. *Jen Munson, Northwestern University; Erin E. Baldinger, University of Minnesota*

Chair: *Kelly A. McKie, University of Delaware*

Discussant: *Hilda Borko, Stanford University*

30.040. The Efficacy of Sound Partners when Implemented by Elementary Tutors: Academic Outcomes and Student Perceptions. SIG-Research in Reading and Literacy; Symposium
Westin Bonaventure, Level 2, Echo Park; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

The Efficacy of Sound Partners when Delivered through Peer Tutors. *Elizabeth Swanson, University of Texas at Austin*
Student Feedback and Perceptions of Cross-age Tutoring. *Emily Mauer, University of Texas at Austin*

A Meta-analysis: Examining the Academic Effects of Cross-age Tutoring. *Andrew Eunghyun Chang, Vanderbilt University*

Chair: *Elizabeth Swanson, University of Texas at Austin*

Discussant: *Erin K. Hogan, University of Louisville*

30.041. Bridging Institutions, Building Futures: School-University Partnerships for Sustainable K-12 CS Education. SIG-School-University Partnership Research; Working Group Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 501A; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Reversing the Turnover-Trust Spiral: Teacher-Led PD and Community Showcases Sustain a School-University Partnership. *Sneha Veeragoudar, University of Massachusetts - Amherst; Keisha L. Green, University of Massachusetts - Amherst*

CT Integration Framework: A Project Investigating Pathways Towards Schoolwide CT Integration. *Heather Sherwood, Education Development Center, Inc.; Cheri Fancsali, Research Alliance for New York City Schools; Babette Moeller, Education Development Center, Inc.*

Teacher and Administrator Perspectives on District-Wide K-12 Computational Thinking Pathways. *Quinn Burke, Digital Promise; Kyle Dunbar, Michigan State University; Merijke Coenraad, Digital Promise Global; Alessandra Rangel, Digital Promise; Sharin R. Jacob, Digital Promise Global; Kelly Mills, Digital Promise Global*

Integrating Mobile App Design with Civic Engagement: An RPP Approach to CSforAll. *Lijun Ni, University at Albany - SUNY; Gillian Bausch; Fred Martin, University of Texas - San Antonio; Bernardo Feliciano, University of Massachusetts - Lowell*

Leveraging Existing Classroom Practices to Integrate

Computational Thinking: An Exploration of K-5 Teacher Learning Trajectories. *Jennifer Albert, The Citadel; Robin Jocius, University of Kentucky; Candace Joswick, University of Texas - Arlington; Melanie Blanton, Texas Tech University; Ian O'Byrne, College of Charleston; Deepthi Joshi, The Citadel*

Novel Pathways to Sustained Equitable Computing Education. *Diane Levitt, Cornell University; Kelly Powers, Cornell Tech; Christopher Hoadley, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Sara Vogel, City University of New York*

Chair: *Chenyang Xu, University of Massachusetts - Amherst*

30.042. Critical and Humanizing Teacher Education for Multilingual Learners: Developing Multilingual Teacher Knowledge Across Contexts. SIG-Second Language Research; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum B; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Transforming Pedagogical Content Knowledge for Teachers of MLLs: Moving Humanizing Pedagogy from Theory to Action. *Megan Madigan Percy, University of Maryland; Francis John Troyan, The Ohio State University; Jessica B Crawford, University of Maryland; Hyerin Ryu, University of Maryland; Daisy Fredricks, Grand Valley State University*

Positioning Practices and Pedagogical Shifts: Early-Career Educators' Development of Linguistic Ideological Clarity in Multilingual Classrooms. *Alissa A. Blair, University of Arkansas at Fayetteville; Lexi Woodward, University of Arkansas*

Preparedness, Knowledge, Self-Efficacy, and Practices of Teacher Candidates of Multilingual Students: Multi-Campus System Comparisons. *Adam Ulysess Coldiron, Washington State University; Yuliya Ardasheva, Washington State University - Tri Cities; Shenghai Dai, Washington State University; Thomas Salisbury, Washington State University; Danica Garcia, Washington State University - Tri-Cities; Yun-Ju Hsiao, Washington State University - Tri-Cities; Onur Ramazan, University of Hong Kong; Gamze Karaer, Washington State University; Lindsay K. Lightner, Washington State University; Anne Marie Guerrettaz, Washington State University; Genoveva Vega, Washington State University*

Above and Beyond Standards: Optimizing Criticality in Preservice Bilingual Teachers Through an Online Dialogic Community. *Eduardo Rafael Munoz-Munoz, San José State University; ash busby, San Jose State University*

Enhancing Pre-Service Teacher Education in Türkiye: Critical Multilingual Language Awareness through Linguistic Landscapes. *Basak Cermikli Ayvaz, Vanderbilt University; Amber N. Warren, Vanderbilt University; Irem Comoglu, Dokuz Eylul University*

Chair: *Kongji Qin, New York University*

Discussant: *Kongji Qin, New York University*

30.043. Reckoning with histories of politics and racialization in STEM Education. SIG-Socio-Political Issues in Mathematics and Science Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 9; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Divided Humanity: Language, Mathematics, and Mexican Racialization in Southern California Schools. *José Francisco Gutiérrez, University of Utah*

Resilience as Resistance or Burden? Black Girls' Critique of Grit, Visibility, and Identity in STEM. *Miranda M. Allen, Texas Tech University*

Race as ideological practice in biology teaching. *Manali J. Sheth, University of Illinois at Chicago*

What Future STEAM Education Should Take and Leave from the History of STEM Education. *Tesha Sengupta-Irving, University of California - Berkeley*

Politics is a Mathematical Act: A Beginning Mathematical Archaeology on the History of School Boards. *Carlos Nicolas Gómez Marchant, University of Texas at Austin; Emma Carene Gargroetzi, University of Texas at Austin*

Chair: *José Francisco Gutiérrez, University of Utah*

Discussant: *Alexis Riley, New York University*

30.044. Assessing How Historical Content is Learned: Research on Student Thinking and Understanding. SIG-Teaching History; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum J; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Does the Anthropocene demand a rethinking of temporal competence in primary history classrooms? *Caitriona Ni Cassaithe, Dublin City University; Anne Marie Kavanagh, Dublin City University*

Marronage as More than Metaphor: AfroLatinx Youths' Ethnoracial Identity Formation in the Third Space. *Eliana Castro, Boston College*

Student Understanding of Disagreements in Societal Controversies about History. *Stephan Venmans, University of Amsterdam; Carla Van Boxtel, University of Amsterdam; Jaap Schuitema, University of Amsterdam; Geerte Maria Savenije, University of Amsterdam; Tessa van Schijndel, University of Amsterdam; Saskia Arbon, University of Amsterdam*

Supporting Historical Thinking in Grades K–2: Insights from iCivics' Private i History Detectives Lessons. *Ryan E. Hughes, University of North Carolina - Greensboro; Katy Field, High Point University*

Understanding U.S. Indigenous History through Cultural-Historical Activity Theory: Insights from Asian American Students. *Yubing Liu, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Chair: *Anna Yonas, University of Kansas*

Discussant: *Chara H. Bohan, Georgia State University*

30.045. Ghosts in the AI Machine: Unforgetting the Artificial Histories Haunting Educational Futures. SIG-Technology as an Agent of Change in Teaching and Learning; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum I; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Data is Power: Positioning K-12 Youth as Participatory, Sociotechnical AI Justice Researchers. *Evan Shieh, Young Data Scientists League; Thema Monroe-White, George Mason University*

Dollar General or Whole Foods? Math Grading Bias as a Warning Sign for AI in Education. *Melissa Warr, New Mexico State University*

Designing a Guide for Equitable AI and Tech Justice in K-12 Education. *Shana Vidal White, Kapor Foundation; Marie K. Heath, Loyola University Maryland*

From Corporate Greenwashing to Thirsty Data Centers: How Young People Analyze GenAI's Environmental Costs. *Charles Logan, Northwestern University*

Chairs: *Marie K. Heath, Loyola University Maryland; Stephanie Smith Budhai, University of Delaware*

Discussant: *Daniel G. Krutka, University of North Texas*

30.046. AI facilitated feedback to support learning. SIG-Technology, Instruction, Cognition & Learning; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Los Feliz; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Designing AI-Facilitated Feedback Using Feedback Triangle Theory. *Jingwen He, University of North Texas; Kui Xie, University of Missouri*

Exploring the Relationship Between Individual Cultural Values and Feedback Literacy Behaviors: A Cross-Country Study. *Mustafa TEPGEÇ, Mustafa Kemal University; Larisa A. Olesova, University of Florida; Joana Heil, University of Mannheim; Heather Rene Woodward, University of Florida; Dirk Ifenthaler, University of Mannheim; Gloria Kim, University of Florida; Kim Copeland, University of Florida*

Feeling and Thinking While Reading: Personalized Emotional Feedback via Automated Facial Recognition Tool. *Yu-San Hsiang, National Yang Ming Chiao Tung University; San Ju Lin, National Yang Ming Chiao Tung University*

Learning Progression-Guided AI Evaluation to Support Feedback on Multimodal Scientific Modeling Tasks. *Leonora Kaldaras, Texas Tech University; Clare Carlson, Michigan State University; Wenxiu Tang, Michigan State University; Tingting Li, Washington State University; Prudence Djagba, Michigan State University; Joseph S. Krajcik, Michigan State University; Kevin Haudek, Michigan State University*

Enabling Student Feedback Literacy through GenAI Feedback:

A Self-regulated Learning Perspective. *Jiahe Gu, The Education University of Hong Kong; Zi Yan, The Education University of Hong Kong*

Chair: *Qi Sun, University at Albany - SUNY*

Discussant: *Anastasia Shikanova, The Ohio State University*

Division and SIG Roundtables

30.047. AERA Roundtable Session Thursday 7:45 am;
Roundtable Session

30.047-1. Black Teachers and Students Historicity, Wake Work and the Struggle Against Erasure (Table 1). SIG-Research Focus on Black Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Affirming Black Histories and Cultures: Black Students' Experiences of Erasure, Belonging, and Self-Actualization. *Tashal Brown, University of Rhode Island; Tiana Freeman, Clark University; Christopher Battle, University of Rhode Island*

Black Students' Emotions Matter Too! Examining How Black Students Feel when Learning Black Historical Suffering. *Brittany Jones, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

Understanding Restorative Justice and the Reproduction of Antiracism in Education. *Kai Butterfield, University of Toronto - OISE*

'We All We Got': Black Teachers Utilizing Peer Relationships as a Form of Wake Work. *British Reynolds, University of Illinois at Chicago; Brittany L. Marshall, San Diego State University*

Chair: *Jawanza Kalonji Rand, Teachers College, Columbia University*

30.047-2. Fugitive Pedagogies and Black Educational Methodologies (Table 2). SIG-Research Focus on Black Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Exploring Anti-Blackness in Education: A Systemic Literature Review with a Focus on Afro-Caribbean College Students. *Faith D. Northern, New York University*

Exploring the Experiences of Black Male Teachers and School Leadership Practices That Influence Retention. *Micah Andre Pate, Prince George's County Public Schools*

"I care about my life and my safety": Recruiting Black Men Teachers in Rural Illinois. *Rachel McMillian, Indiana University - Indianapolis; Nathaniel Bryan, University of Texas at Austin*

Reimagining Resistance: Intimate Pedagogies and the Black Movement 1964-1985. *Jasmine Norma Watson,*

Pennsylvania State University

The Complexity of Developing Properly Trained Education Professionals for African American Children: Exploring an African-Based Indigenous Socialization Process. *Kmt G. Shockley, University of Houston*

Chair: *Judith I. Brooks-Buck, J. Brooks-Buck Educational Consulting*

Discussant: *Sheree Nicole Alexander, Atlantic City School District*

30.047-3. Knowledge Network, Teacher Agency, and Systemic Changes (Table 3). SIG-Educational Change; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Change strategies in undergraduate STEM education: A meta-synthesis and update of a decade of research. *Ying Wang, FHI 360; Rachel L. Renbarger, FHI 360; Taylor Boyd, Western Michigan University; Emily Bolger, Michigan State University; Noah Finkelstein, University of Colorado - Boulder; Charles R. Henderson, Western Michigan University; Scott P. Simkins, North Carolina A&T State University; Andrea L. Beach, Western Michigan University; M. Danny Caballero, Michigan State University*

From Achievement to Purpose: Educating Beyond Academic Success. *Mary Anne Heng, National Institute of Education, Nanyang Technological University*

Teachers as Change Agents: Exploring the Possibilities of Teacher Agency in a Test-Centered Education System. *Jina Ro, Sungkyunkwan University*

Chair: *Jina Ro, Sungkyunkwan University*

30.047-4. Parent, child, and schools: Promoting connections (Table 4). SIG-Family, School, Community Partnerships; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Parental Perceptions of Homework and Its Impact on Family Stress: A Mixed Methods Study of Single-Parent and Two-Parent Households. *Jessica McCormick, University of Pittsburgh - Greensburg; Natalie Conrad Barnyak, University of Pittsburgh - Johnstown*

Unpacking Parental Intentions in the Home Math Environment: A Regression Analysis of Malleable Predictors. *Zhengqing Li, University of Denver*

Facilitating Dual Capacity-Building Partnerships between Teachers and Families in Early Childhood Education. *Jadyn Laixely, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Zhiyue Lu, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Tina Smith-Bonahue, University of Florida; Erin E. Reid, Erikson Institute; Stephanie C. Sanders-Smith, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Chair: *Kyle Elizabeth Miller, Illinois State University*

30.047-5. Promoting family-school engagement (Table 5). SIG-Family, School, Community Partnerships; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Unseen Journeying: Latinx Mothers' Experience and Navigation of Pre-Referral Home-School Collaboration. *Yone Rodriguez, Claremont Graduate University*

Perspectives Over Time: Communication Between Parents and Teachers of Students With Disabilities (2017–2022). *Leslie Ann Rogers, Montana State University; Sally Slipher, Montana State University*

“It Starts at Home”: Understanding School Staff Perspectives on Family Engagement in Trauma-Informed Practices. *Megumi Grace Hine, Washington University in St. Louis; Margaret K. Powers, Washington University in St. Louis; Erica Ellsworth Miller, Washington University in St. Louis; Sophie C. Song, Washington University in St. Louis*

Establishing a Practically-Informed Agenda for Research to Transform Family, School, and Community Partnership. *Shana J. Haines, University of Vermont; Kristin Vogel-Campbell, North Point Educational Service Center; Holly M. Kreider, National Association for Family, School and Community Engagement; Maggie Caspe, New York University; Jacqueline Lynch, Florida International University; Veronica Kang, University of Maryland; Megumi Grace Hine, Washington University in St. Louis; Stephany Cuevas, Chapman University; Lori Delale-O'Connor, University of Pittsburgh; Cristina C. Santamaria Graff, Indiana University - Indianapolis; Susana Beltran-Grimm, Portland State University; Judy Paulick, University of Virginia; Nicole Megan Edwards, Rowan University; Thomas J Capretta, The Ohio State University; Parker Goss, University of Vermont*

Chair: *Linxi Lu, University of Chicago*

30.047-6. Freirean Praxis on Humanizing Education (Table 6). SIG-Paulo Freire; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

A Freirean Reckoning with AI and Capitalism in the Pursuit of Humanizing Education. *Tiffany Karalis Noel, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Courtney Doxbeck, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

A Liberatory Learning Approach for Digital Transformation in Baixada Fluminense Favelas. *Armando J. Torres, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Samantha A. Lindgren, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Paulo Freire and the Southeast Asian Overseas Chinese Student Labor Pipeline in Taiwan. *Chen-Wei Chang, National Taiwan Normal University*

Chair: *Richard V. Kahn, Antioch University*

30.047-7. Queer Pedagogies and Leading The Future: Rurality and Discontinuity (Table 7). SIG-Queer Studies;

Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Educators Making Time Matter: Queer Pedagogies of Discontinuity, Futurity, and Anachronism. *Avner Rogel, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Pedagogy of Pride in Rural Schools: A Review of Rural Education & Queer Identities. *Amy Price Azano, Virginia Tech; Clint D. Whitten, Virginia Tech*

30.047-8. Transforming Queer and Trans Research: Youth, Bridge Building, Cultivating Spaces (Table 8). SIG-Queer Studies; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Exploring the Queer Potentiality of Messiness in Education. *Zander Nowell, University of Colorado - Boulder*

"I Didn't Feel Safe": Intersectional Tracking of Queer Students of Color. *Sonny Partola, University of Wisconsin - Stevens Point; Leticia Alvarez Gutiérrez, University of Utah*

Learning from the Spaces in Between a Bridge Building Imaginary of Asian-Jotória Coalition. *Vivian Bo Kyung Lee, University of Utah*

30.047-9. Instructional Innovation and Learner Outcomes in PE/PETE (Table 9). SIG-Research on Learning and Instruction in Physical Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Did You Understand the Game? Strengthening Oral Explanations of Physical Education Teachers Through Coherence-Building Aids. *Tim Heemsoth, Europa-Universität Flensburg; Rieke Frerichs, Europa-Universität Flensburg*

Effects of a structured sports program on motor skills and executive functions in preschoolers: A pilot randomized controlled trial. *Yujia Qu, The Education University Of Hong Kong; Jiayang Luo, China Institute of Sports Science; King Chung Derwin CHAN, The Education University Of Hong Kong; Jiawei Li, Macau University of Science and Technology*

Evaluating ChatGPT Accuracy in Answering a Basketball Common Content Knowledge Test in Physical Education. *Omar Albaloul, Kuwait University; Chad Killian, University of New Hampshire*

High school students' experiences and perspectives of group processing in Physical Education classes. *Ben Dyson,*

University of North Carolina - Greensboro; Yongjin Lee, University of North Carolina - Greensboro; Lars Bjørke, Inland Norway University; Seunghyun Baek, SUNY - College at Cortland; Judy A. Fowler, University of North Carolina - Greensboro

Teaching in 360 Degrees: Virtual Reality to Prepare Teachers for Behavior Management in Physical Education. *Luke Parker, Australian Catholic University; Renata Cinelli, Australian Catholic University*

Chair: *Cory Elijah Dixon, Rowan University*

30.047-10. Nurturing Social-Emotional Learning Through the Arts (Table 10). SIG-Arts and Learning; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Building Arts-Based Social-Emotional Learning Practices Through Embodied Professional Learning. *Yorel Lashley, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Erica Rosenfeld Halverson, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Stephanie Richards, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Emily Nott, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Tracey Bullington, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Lindsey Kourafas, University of Wisconsin - Madison; John Louis Samuels, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Leila Rahnamanoabadi, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Art Therapy Approaches Integrating Social-Emotional Learning for the Mental Health of East Asian International Students.

Eunhye Bae, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign

Through the Lens of Self-Efficacy: Perspectives of College Art Majors and Educators in South Korea and China on Ethical Awareness of AI Art Creation. *Sori Kim, Teachers College, Columbia University; Siyao Lyu, Columbia University; Sung-ah Jun, Sahmyook University; Yadi Liu, China Academy of Art*

Exploring Preschool Story Time: The Influence of Teacher Self-Efficacy and Developmental Beliefs on Drama-Based Strategies. *Melissa Pierce, Arizona State University; Scott C. Marley, Arizona State University; Lauren van Huisstede, Arizona State University; Katie Bernstein, Arizona State University; Jenny Millinger, Childsplay Theatre Company; M. Adelaida Restrepo, University of South Florida; Michael F. Kelley, Arizona State University; Erin Rotheram-Fuller, Arizona State University; Annette Schmidt, Arizona State University*

Place and Kids as Coteachers in Developing Diverse and Expansive Conceptions of the Arts. *Naomi Field, Northwestern University; Megan Bang, Northwestern University*

Chair: *Eunhye Bae, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

30.048. AERA Roundtable Session Thursday 7:45 am; Roundtable Session

30.048-1. Leadership Preparation, Mentoring, and Development (Table 1). Division A - Administration; Roundtable Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Developing School Leadership Through Sustained Mentoring and Coaching: A Longitudinal Qualitative Single-Case Study. *Minoo Mohammadi, Texas A&M University; Beverly J. Irby, Texas A&M University; Rafael Lara-Alecio, Texas A&M University; Cindy L. Guerrero, Texas A&M University; Linda Rodriguez, Texas A&M University; Fuhui Tong, Texas A&M University*

Three Levels of Leadership Development for Diversifying the Teacher Profession. *Alex Guzman, Kean University*

Teacher Leadership Identity Formation: The Interaction Effect of Professional Development and School Climate. *Peter Wiens, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Seoyeon Park, University of Nevada, Las Vegas*

Chair: *Jerry Ray Burkett, University of North Texas at Dallas*

30.048-2. Leadership Strategies During Crisis and Emergency Situations (Table 2). Division A - Administration; Roundtable Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

One Crisis After Another: Leading Through Natural Disasters and Health Pandemics. *Kessa Roberts, Clemson University; Cheyenne Phillips, Southern Methodist University; Shanae Neal, Southern Methodist University; Shanae Neal, Southern Methodist University; Alexandra E. Pavlakis, Southern Methodist University; Meredith Paige Richards, Southern Methodist University*

Leading Through Crises with Emotional Intelligence and Critical Consciousness. *Charo D. Darwin, Claremont Graduate University*

Educational Leaders Navigating Polarization and Conflict to Create Positive Future Change: A Vertical Development Study. *Jennifer Ouellette-Schramm, Walden University*

Chair: *Huang Wu, University of Missouri - Kansas City*

30.048-3. Structural Approaches to Teacher Retention, Organizational Improvement, and Partnership Formation (Table 3). Division A - Administration; Roundtable Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

A Review of Research on Teacher Turnover in China: from the Perspective of School Leadership. *Robert Przybylski, Wenzhou-Kean University; Manqi Lin, Wenzhou-Kean University; Huixin Wang, Wenzhou-Kean University*

Development and Implementation of a System Infrastructure for Community Schooling. *Nadia M. Sabat Bass, University of California - Los Angeles; Marisa Saunders, University of California - Los Angeles*

How Can Family and School Cooperate: A Study on the Institutional Construction of Family-School Cooperation in Chinese Primary Schools. *Chuanyou Bao, Beijing Normal University; Yuting Wang, Beijing Normal University*

Negotiating Innovation: Legitimacy, Asymmetry, and Disruption in Interorganizational Partnerships. *Jay Paredes Scribner, Old Dominion University; Karen L. Sanzo, Old Dominion University; Gary Skeen, Old Dominion University; Stephen Croffie-Djan, Old Dominion University*

Student Voice as a Catalyst for School Reforms: Enhancing Educational Effectiveness Across High School Settings. *Nai-Ying Whang, National Taiwan Normal University*

Chair: *Joan Schumann, International MTSS Association*

30.048-4. Leadership Perspectives: Learning from Leaders' Beliefs and Sensemaking During Reform (Table 4).

Division A - Administration; Roundtable Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Blessing or Curse?: School and system leaders' emotional responses to implementing Michigan's Partnership Model. *Sarah L. Woulfin, University of Texas at Austin; Daniel Dawer, University of Texas at Austin; Lizeth I. Lizarraga, University of Texas at Austin; Jeremy L. Singer, University of Michigan-Flint*

Continuous Improvement Coaches as Sensemakers and Sensegivers. *Parker Morse Andreoli, Clemson University; Carlos Sandoval, Clemson University*

Exploring pre-service administrators' perceptions of the conditions needed to improve schools. *Chad Lochmiller, Indiana University*

Restorative Justice in a Florida School District: Leaders Sensemaking and Sensegiving. *Hilary Lustick, University of Massachusetts - Lowell; Alounso A. Gilzene, Florida State University*

Stigmatization or Targeted Support for Improvement? (Self-)Perceptions of Schools Serving Disadvantaged Communities. *Denise Demski, Ruhr-Universität Bochum; Björn Hermstein, Ostfalia University of Applied Sciences; Johannes Lüneneschloß, Ostfalia University of Applied Sciences*

Chair: *Madhu Narayanan, Florida International University*

30.048-5. Reimagining the Holders of Knowledge: Teachers and Youth as (Co)llaborators and (Co)creators in the Pursuit of Educational Justice and Renewal (Table 5).

Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 7:45-

9:15am

Participants:

- A Participatory Program Review to Strengthen a Youth Development Program Serving Under-Resourced Communities. *Daina Estime, The Possible Zone; Salma Yehia, The Possible Zone*
- Counter-mapping School Wellbeing with Youth in Alternative Education Programs: Love Notes to Liminal Space. *Auralia Brooke, University of New Brunswick*
- “We Just Don’t Have the Time”: Gesturing Towards Temporal Autonomy through an Intergenerational Learning Community. *Lucy A. Robins, Graduate Center - CUNY*
- “You mean down here?”: Ethnic Studies, Social Studies, White Pre-Service Teachers and the American South. *Brian C. Gibbs, Georgia College & State University*
- Critical, Iterative Autobiography: Blending history, lived experience, and imagined futures in an undergraduate foundations course (15/15). *Daniela Harton, University of Colorado - Boulder*

30.048-6. Remembering and Reimagining Black Communities and the Role of Black Education in the Pursuit of Educational Justice and Renewal (Table 6). Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

- Black Male Black-Male-Centered Counter-spaces: Utilizing Abolitionist Teaching & Black Trans Feminist to Disrupt Patriarchal Norms. *Gene F. McAdoo, University of California - Los Angeles; Seth Duncan, University of California - Los Angeles*
- Connecting Place and Progress: The Role of Critical Place-Based Learning, Public History and Culturally Sustainable Pedagogical Practices. *Brandon J. Beck, University of Maryland Baltimore County*
- Leveraging Past Experiences to Imagine Futures: Black Young Men’s Mattering in a High School Partnership. *Lauren M Strickland, University of Delaware; Roderick L. Carey, University of Delaware; Sofina Shekhar, University of Delaware*
- Looking Back to Look Forward: Applying Sankofa to the Teaching of Black Los Angeles. *Stephanie Renee Anckle, City of Long Beach; Mia Glionna, Cerritos College*

Chair: *Charles T. Young, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

30.048-7. Curriculum in collaboration: Exploring multilingual family and community literacy practices as resources for curriculum development (Table 7). Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Promoting Trilingual Development: An Examination of Family Support in a Child’s Multilingual Trajectory. *Mihaela Gazioglu, Westfield State University*

“It was so close to home, we couldn’t deny it.” Co-Designing Climate Justice Curriculum with Multilingual families. *Wisam Sedawi, University of Michigan; Angela Calabrese, University of Michigan*

Spiritual Multilingualism in Black Muslim Community Literacies. *Kaha Abdi, The Ohio State University*

Mediating Multilingualism: Chinese Families’ Transnational Practices in Dual Language Education. *SooJin Jeon, Teachers College, Columbia University; Patricia Martínez-Alvarez, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Verbal Interactions and Engagement in Shared Reading: A Bilingual Chinese American Family’s Literacy Practices. *Shuling Yang, University of Maryland - Baltimore County*

Narrating Futures, Remembering Roots: Immigrant Family Literacy Practices and Dual Language Learners’ Narrative Skills. *Mayu Lindblad, University of California - Davis; Maria Belen Buttiler, University of California - Davis*

Chair: *Emma R. Britton, University of Missouri - St. Louis*

Discussant: *Emma R. Britton, University of Missouri - St. Louis*

30.048-8. Educational Research in Precarious Times (Table 8). Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

- Deportation dialogue: Pláticas and movidas as strategies for sociocultural critique. *Christopher L. Milk Bonilla, Texas State University; Brenda Rubio, University of North Texas*
- Impacts of COVID on home insecure Black mothers: Education challenges and strategies to move forward. *Margarita Daza Murcia, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Tehia Starker Glass, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Kendra Jason, University of North Carolina - Charlotte*
- Intersectional Organizing and Transformative Solidarity in Educational Justice Movements. *Mark R. Warren, University of Massachusetts - Boston; Vajra M. Watson, University of Redlands; Shaun de Vera, California State University - Sacramento; Bianca Ortiz-Wythe, University of Massachusetts - Boston*

Narratives of Belonging: Women and Racially/Ethnically Diverse Students in Mathematical Spaces. *Seyda Uysal, University of Southern Mississippi*

Chair: *Pheather R. Harris, University of California - Irvine*

30.048-9. Reimagining Preparation Programs for Equity and Social Justice Leaders (Table 9). SIG-Leadership for Social Justice; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Reimagining Doctoral Education: Designing an Equity-Centered EdD for Future Educational Leaders. *Shana Matamala, University of LaVerne; Andrea Minkoff, University of La Verne*

Using Role Plays to Develop Administrative Candidates who Lead for Equity. *Abebayehu Aemero Tekleselassie, The George Washington University; Rebecca Ann Thessin, The George Washington University; Jennifer K. Clayton, The George Washington University; Timothy Drake, North Carolina State University; Leslie Trimmer, The George Washington University; Shaun D Shepard, The George Washington University*

Developing Social Justice Leadership Competence to Address Opportunity Gaps: Results from a Simulations Intervention. *Daniel Moraguez, Florida State University; Secil Caskurlu, Florida State University; Ravi Bhatt, Florida State University; Seunghee Park, Florida State University*

Chair: *Natasha N. Johnson, Augusta University*

30.048-10. Language, Decoloniality And Social Justice (Table 10). SIG-Decolonial, Postcolonial, and Anti-Colonial Studies in Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Decolonising Language Policy: Insights from the Global North and Global South. *Giovanni E. Whyte, University of North Dakota; Elvis ResCue, University of Birmingham*

Decolonizing English Language teacher education: The role of Testimonios in navigating Social Justice in English Language Teacher Education in the Global South. *Macarena Durán, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile*

From South to West Africa: Coloniality of Language Policy and Epistemic Silence, Violence, and Injustice. *Mfundo Jabulani Msimango, Pennsylvania State University; Mariam Yasmine Noura Jeanne N'diaye, Pennsylvania State University*

Language, Power, and Pedagogy: Challenging the Legacy of Colonial Literacy in South African Township Schools. *Mfundo Jabulani Msimango, Pennsylvania State University*

“Bread-earning Saturated with Humiliation”: Palestinian English Teachers Navigating Love, Language, and Resistance in Jewish schools. *Muzna Awayed-Bishara, Tel Aviv University*

Chair: *Gayoung Choi, University of Nebraska - Lincoln*

30.049. AERA Roundtable Session Thursday 7:45 am - Gold 1; Roundtable Session

30.049-1. Understanding and Supporting Black and Hispanic Faculty (Table 1). Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Full, free, and unapologetic: Black women faculty navigating the tensions of full professorship promotion. *Danielle Magasano, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Rachelle Winkle-Wagner, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Not All Birds Flock Together? Intersectional Homophily Within the Social Support Networks of Black Women Faculty. *Paris D. Wicker, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Rachelle Winkle-Wagner, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Bridget J. Goosby, University of Texas at Austin*

Remembering to Reimagine: Black and Hispanic Engineering Faculty Experiences with the Tenure and Promotion Process. *Henry Tran, University of South Carolina; Spencer Platt, University of South Carolina; Maria L. Espino, University of California - Los Angeles; Ta'lia Gordon, University of South Carolina; Brian Le, University of California - Los Angeles*

Barriers to Equity, Diversity, Inclusion, and Accessibility in Online Higher Education Teaching. *Julia Forgie, University of Toronto; Heidi Kenkel, University of Toronto - OISE; Avery Chien, University of Toronto*

Chair: *Henry Tran, University of South Carolina*

30.049-2. Teaching at the Intersections: Language, Culture, and Equity in Multilingual Classrooms (Table 2). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Building Mathematical Foundations for Multilingual Learners through Translanguaging and Modern Classrooms Project: An Action Research. *Cynthia Elizabeth Rodriguez, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Woomee Kim, George Mason University*

Diversity Celebration or Mainstream Assimilation: How Could Culturally Relevant Content be Taught in a Culturally Relevant Way? *Katrina Liu, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Kody Lightfoot, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Elsa Lopez, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*

Integrating Language and Content: Supporting Secondary Teachers Through Explicit Literacy Instruction in Mainstream Classrooms & Beyond. *Stephanie Coca, Oklahoma State University; Qiuying Wang, Oklahoma State University*

Reimagining Bilingual Teacher Preparation: Attributional Beliefs and Culturally Responsive Self-Efficacy as Pathways to Equity. *Linnie Greenlees, Texas Tech University; Delia Carrizales, Texas Tech University; Denise Lara, Texas A&M University - Corpus Christi; Weverton Ataíde Pinheiro, Texas Tech University; Fernando Valle, Texas Tech University*

A Case Study of Teachers' Adaptations of the Mathematics Language Routine Stronger & Clearer. *Sarah Ann Roberts, University of California - Santa Barbara; Royce Olarte, University of California - Santa Barbara; Evelyn Margarita*

Vera-Flandez, University of California - Santa Barbara;
Hyeyeon Han, University of California - Santa Barbara;
Vincent Robinson, University of California - Santa Barbara;
Grace Rincon Garcia, University of California - Santa
Barbara

Chair: IHSAN GHAZAL, Boston university

Discussant: Sen Wang, Boston University

30.049-3. Moments That Matter: Teacher Identities Across Generations (Table 3). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Becoming a Teacher: Moments That Matter. *Alexandria Holmes, Purdue University*

Creating Space: Early Career MotherScholars Building Community in Urban Teacher Education. *Heather F. Clark, California State University - Dominguez Hills; Yoonjin Nam-Huh, California State University - Dominguez Hills; Sara Jasmin Diaz-Montejano, University of California - Los Angeles*

The Apprenticeship of Observation at 50: How We Have Studied K-12 Experiences and What We Have Learned. *William J. Davis, Southern Utah University*

Twitch Zoomers as Early Career Educators: How the COVID-19 Generation Perceives Their Unique Teaching Strengths. *Amy L. Ardell, Mount Saint Mary's University; Nancy T. Walker, University of La Verne; Margaret Saucedo Curwen, Chapman University; Laurie MacGillivray, University of Memphis*

Why Gen-Z Is Choosing the Classroom: Motivations of Beginning Teachers. *Gabriella Macri, Montclair State University; Rebecca Myers, Montclair State University; Helenrose Fives, Montclair State University; Nicole Barnes, American Psychological Association*

Chair: *Gabriella Macri, Montclair State University*

30.049-4. Teaching Beyond the Formula: Culturally Responsive Approaches to STEM and Student Success (Table 4). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Improving Culturally Responsive Practices in High School Classrooms through Teacher Professional Development: A Mixed-Method Study. *Robin Wisniewski, RTI International; Yihua Hong, RTI International; Francesca López, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Ceri Dean, Dean Education Consulting; Jill Pierce, Research Triangle Institute; Jon Boyette, RTI International*

Longitudinal Exploration of Teachers' Culturally Sustaining Pedagogy after Training and then Delivering Ethnic-Racial

Identity Curricula. *Megan Satterthwaite-Freiman, Harvard University; Adriana J. Umaña-Taylor, Harvard University; Guicheng Tan, Harvard University; Sophie Hölscher, Martin Luther University Halle-Wittenberg; Ishani Parekh, University of Oxford; Keshav Bhatt, Self-employed; Shoba Ramanadhan, Harvard University*

Teacher Competencies to Improve Experiences and Outcomes for Diverse Learners. *Sara H. Petit-McClure, Syracuse University*

Utilizing Culturally and Historically Responsive Teaching and Learning Towards Humanizing Science Instruction. *Vanessa Nizeyimana Louis, University of Michigan*

Chair: *Thursica Kovinthan Levi, Toronto Metropolitan University*

Discussant: *Thursica Kovinthan Levi, Toronto Metropolitan University*

30.049-5. Language, Power, and Identity in Teacher Preparation: Multilingual Awareness, Academic Language, and Intersectionality (Table 5). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Clinical Simulations as Sites for Advancing Critical Multilingual Language Awareness. *Jessica Fundalinski, Syracuse University*

Examining Dispositions for Multilingual Learners: A Comparative Case Study of Three Pre-service Teachers. *Jared McKee, University of Florida; Mark B. Pacheco, University of Florida*

Exploring Early Career Teachers' Beliefs and Practices Around Academic Language for English Learner Students. *Sunny Li, Syracuse University; Louise C. Wilkinson, Syracuse University*

From Stance to Struggle: How Pre-Service Teachers Perceive Possibilities and Limits of Translanguaging. *Weronika Kaczmarczyk-Smith, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Preparing Future Teachers for Intersectionality Through an Interdisciplinary Webinar on Multilingualism and Disability. *Woongsik Choi, Illinois State University; Melissa McGraw, Illinois State University; Christina S. Gilhuber, Europa-Universität Flensburg*

Chair: *Sunny Li, Syracuse University*

30.049-6. Professional Development and Praxis: Innovations within Asian Contexts (Table 6). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Agency in Isolation: An Ethnographic Study of Rural Teachers' Self-Directed Professional Development in China. *Meina Zhu, Wayne State University; Zixi Li, Indiana University*

Explore the Potential Meaning of STE(A)M Education: Teachers' Perceptions in a Chinese Context. *Zhuoyue Shao, East China Normal University; Hui Liu, Zhejiang University*

Inclusive Education Climate and Teachers' Differentiated Instruction in China: Role of Teachers' Efficacy and Attitudes. *Wangqian Fu, Beijing Normal University*

Optimizing Teaching Research Activities in Chinese Primary Schools through Change Laboratory: A Case Study. *Chunting Diao, Hubei University of Chinese Medicine*

Unpacking the Role of Reflection in Enacting Equity-Centered Practice: Evidence from Singapore. *Wen-Chia Claire Chang, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University*

30.049-7. Situated, Sustained, and Transformative: Innovations in Teacher Apprenticeship and Preparation (Table 7). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Centering a Culture of Care in Teacher Residency Programs. *Lisa Merrill, American Institutes for Research; Victoria M. Theisen-Homer, Northern Arizona University; Jessica Manzone, Northern Arizona University*

From Band-Aids to Blueprints: High-Quality Teacher Residencies as the National Standard for Teacher Apprenticeships. *Aisha Haynes Young, Prepared To Teach/New York University*

Job Satisfaction in Focus: Photovoice with Teachers in Arts-Integrated Schools. *Sarah Byrne Bausell, North Carolina State University; Marie Himes, North Carolina State University*

Situated, Relational, Transformative: Reimagining Teacher Preparation for the Early Childhood Workforce. *Foram Bhukhanwala, Arcadia University*

What Works?: The Role of Partner School Leadership in Advancing High-Quality Teacher Residency Programs. *GoMee Park, University of Texas - Rio Grande Valley; Lileana Rios-Ledezma, University of Texas Rio Grande Valley; Zulmaris Diaz, University of Texas - Rio Grande Valley*

Chair: *Hartley Banack, University of Northern British Columbia*
Discussant: *Saroja Warner, Wested*

30.049-8. Ethics in Motion: Identity, Reflexivity, and Teacher Praxis (Table 8). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Examining preservice teachers' morality and moral education in China: A mixed research approach. *Gang Zhu, East China Normal University*

Exploring teachers' enactment of PE core competency curriculum policy in China: Insights from policy roles and sense-making. *Gang Zhu, East China Normal University*

Reflections in Motion: Video Dialogue Between Mother and Teacher-Daughter as Resistance to Scripted Mandates. *Terri L. Hubbard, Polk State College & University of South Florida; Ilene R. Berson, University of South Florida; Michael J. Berson, University of South Florida*

The White Researcher/Savior: The Messy Contradictions of Critical Antiracist Research in Education. *Maeve Wall, California State University - Northridge; Zachary A. Casey, Rhodes College*

Unpacking Elementary Teachers' Digital Transformation Competence: A Profile Analysis and the Role of School Support. *Woo-jeong Shim, Hannam University; Jeong-a Kim, Korean Educational Development Institute; Jiyoung Ha, Yonsei University*

Chair: *Gang Zhu, East China Normal University*

30.049-9. Emotional Landscapes of Teaching: Resilience, Labor, and Support (Table 9). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Longitudinal Relationships Between Job Demands-Resources and Teachers' Spiritual Resilience: Evidence from RI-CLPM Analysis. *Junying Lu, The Education University of Hong Kong; Junjun Chen, Education University of Hong Kong; Hao Li, University of Hong Kong; Kwok Kuen Tsang, The Education University of Hong Kong*

Revising Emotional Labor in Teaching: When Marxist Alienation Meets Internationalist Agency. *Kwok Kuen Tsang, The Education University of Hong Kong; Ying Zhang, Purdue University; Guanyu Li, Center for Teacher Education Research; Huan Song, Beijing Normal University*

Teachers' Moodprints In the Workplace: Emotional Regulation Through, For and With Others. *Chloe B. Le, University of Louisiana at Lafayette; Anh Ngoc Quynh Phan, University of Kent*

The Path to Job Satisfaction: Emotional Intelligence and Trust Among Teachers. *Zheng Lin, 岭南大学; Jing Huang, Lingnan University*

Seeing Failure Through Teachers' Eyes: What Makes a Student Failure Memorable? *Xinyu S. Pan, Bank Street College of Education; Xiaolin Ou, Teachers College, Columbia University; Mincong Wu, Teachers College, Columbia University*

30.050. AERA Roundtable Session Thursday 7:45 am - Gold 2; Roundtable Session

30.050-1. Educating for Democracy in International Contexts

(Table 1). SIG-Democratic Citizenship in Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Educating for Democracy: Primary Students' Attitudes Towards Democratic Values and Their Relationship with Civic Knowledge. *Lianne Hoek, University of Amsterdam; Anne Bert Dijkstra, University of Amsterdam*

Teacher Agency in Handling Controversial Issues in South African Classrooms. *Judy L. Pace, University of San Francisco*

The Changing Landscape of Good Citizenship in Hong Kong: Government Narratives and Educational Implications. *Jason Cong Lin, The Education University of Hong Kong*

Learning Knowledge or Participation in Civic Activity?: What can be done to promote students' future civic engagement at school? *Shinui Kim, Johns Hopkins University*

Chair: *Jie Lin, Shanghai Jiao Tong University*

30.050-2. Rural Students Reimagined: Identity, Belonging, and Access in Higher Education (Table 2). SIG-Rural Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

ActiveFlex Learning: Bridging the Rural-Urban Divide in Higher Education Access Through Flexible, Engaged Pedagogical Innovation. *Katherine R. Kandalec Holm, Athens State University; Mark Gale, Athens State University*

STEM Decisions in Context: Identity and Meaning Making among Rural Black Undergraduate Students. *Shannon Clark, University of Georgia; Michael M. Barger, University of Georgia; Emily Quinn Rosenzweig, Teachers College, Columbia University; Paula P. Lemons, University of Georgia*

Supporting Rural Scholars: A Case Study Examining Students' Experiences and Perceptions of Rural Support Programs. *William Redding, University of Georgia*

Support Systems in Graduate School: Experiences of Low-income, Academically Talented, First Generation Engineering Masters' Students in a Rural State. *Rafael L da Silva, Boise State University; Sharon Whightsil, Boise State University; Lisa A Giacumo, George Mason University; Arvin Farid, Boise State University*

The Influences of a Rural-Focused Study Abroad Course on Undergraduate Students' Place-Based Identity Development. *Josh Thompson, Virginia Tech*

Chair: *Malani C Hoffpauir, University of Louisiana at Lafayette*

30.050-3. Advancing Instructional Practices for Students with Disabilities (Table 3). SIG-Special and Inclusive Education Research; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;

7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Towards Critically Inclusive Classrooms: Patterns and Predictors of U.S. Elementary Teachers' Curricular Modification Priorities. *Sarah A Caroleo, Brown University*
Understanding our Impact: A Social Network Analysis of Early Reading Intervention Leadership for Students with Disabilities. *Sarah Irvine Belson, American University; Danielle Gervais Sodani, American University; Anne Murphy Karabell, American University; Becky Nolin, District of Columbia Public Schools*

Don't Forget About Working Memory: Professionals' Consideration of Working Memory and Basic Reading Skills Interventions for Students With or at Risk for Having a Learning Disability. *David Antunes, Rutgers University*
Empowering Exceptional Minds through Self-Determination. *Sunaira Tejpar, Queen's University - Kingston; Julia Hale, Queen's University - Kingston; Ian A. Matheson, Queen's University - Kingston*

Chair: *David D. Yang, Western Washington University*

30.050-4. Centering Neurodivergent Voices and Perspectives in Education (Table 4). SIG-Special and Inclusive Education Research; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

When Inclusion Excludes: DisCrit Insights into the Racialized and Medicalized Framing of Neurodiversity. *Chelsea Tracy-Bronson, Stockton University; Sara Scribner, Plymouth State University*

Belonging through design: Neurodivergent co-designers reflect on their experiences in an informal STEM internship. *Wendy B. Martin, Education Development Center, Inc.; Samantha Tumolo, Education Development Center, Inc.; Susan M. Letourneau, New York Hall of Science; Ariana Riccio Arista, Education Development Center, Inc.*

Listening Bodies, Cold Calls, and the Burden of Existing: #Neurodivergent Students' Perspectives on School. *Dana Baker, Fairleigh Dickinson University*

Neurodivergent-affirmative teaching practices in the context of STEAM and beyond. *Corey Reutlinger, Arizona State University; Margarita Pivovarova, Arizona State University; Mirka E. Koro, Arizona State University; Seth Thorn, Arizona State University; Anani M. Vasquez, Neurodiversity Education Research Center; Robert Stenson, University of Jamestown; Denise Ripps, Rethink Microschools*

Beyond Equal Access: Reconceptualizing Educational Equity Through Neurodiversity-Affirming Pedagogy in Special Education. *Holly Haynes, Truett McConnell University; Julian Gonzalez, The Jacob's Ladder Group; Amy O'Dell, The Jacob's Ladder Group*

Chair: *Sarah D. Lent, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

30.050-5. Self-Study as Acumen for Advancing Teacher Education Practices: Cultivating a Path of Empowerment within Supervision (Table 5). SIG-Self-Study of Teacher Education Practices; Roundtable Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Self-Study as Acumen for Advancing Teacher Education Practices: Cultivating a Path of Empowerment within Supervision. *Raven Robinson-Wilson, University of North Florida; Shaundricka Medlock, University of North Florida; Jeania Jones, University of North Florida*

Addressing Encumberment in Supervision: Black Teacher Educator as Broker for Change. *Raven Robinson-Wilson, University of North Florida*

Stirring the Pot: Understanding Black Leadership, Culture, and Boundary-Spanning through the Metaphor of Roux. *Shaundricka Medlock, University of North Florida*

Resilience of a Black Woman: Journey through the Racial Mismatch Land of Supervision. *Jeania Jones, University of North Florida*

Chair: *Raven Robinson-Wilson, University of North Florida*

Discussant: *Raven Robinson-Wilson, University of North Florida*

30.050-6. Posthuman Encounters with Educational Technologies (Table 6). SIG-Critical Posthuman and Postfoundational Studies in Education; Roundtable Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Posthumanist Pedagogy for Early Childhood Educational Technology: Entangled Moments with Educational Robots. *Sung Eun Jung, University of Arizona; Sung Ryung Lyu, American University; Seongryeong Yu, Old Dominion University*

Recognizing Digital Technology as Educational Actor: A Sociomaterial Perspective on Remote Teaching. *Woomok Jeong, University of Wisconsin - Madison; YangHyun Kim, City University of New York; Alex Kumi-Yeboah, University at Albany - SUNY*

Reconceptualizing Informal Learner-GenAI Relations: A Posthumanist Intra-action Framework. *Tianxing Feng, University of Georgia*

Staying-With Discomfort: AI, Whiteness, and Ethical Disorientation in Participatory Fieldwork. *Sarah Cornette, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*

Reimagining Art Pedagogy in the Age of AI: Sensory-Algorithmic Dialogic Learning. *Hsin Fang, Florida State University; Jiayi Guo, University of Georgia*

Chair: *MaryJohn R. Pachuta-Rysak, Grand Valley State University*

30.050-7. From Empathy to Action: Emotional, Restorative, and Creative Pathways in Teacher Preparation (Table 7). SIG-Critical Educators for Social Justice; Roundtable

Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Exploring Compassion, Empathy, and Social Justice in Preservice Teachers: A Moderated Mediation Approach. *Megan Hut, West Virginia University; D. Jake Follmer, West Virginia University*

Joy as a Political Emotion in Mathematics Education. *Eric Cordero-Siy, Boston University; Gregory Benoit, Boston University; Aaron Brakoniecki, Boston University*

Teaching Restorative Justice in Preservice Teacher Education: Pathways for Healing and Mitigating Violence in Schools. *Ardavan Eizadirad, Wilfrid Laurier University; Crystena Parker-Shandal, University of Waterloo*

Thinking like an Author: Nurturing Bilingual Preservice Teachers' Creative Resistance through Arts-Based Ethnic Studies Pedagogies. *Michelle Soto-Peña, California Polytechnic State University, Pomona; Arturo Nevarez, California State University - Stanislaus; Luis Genaro Garcia, California State University - Sacramento*

30.050-8. Healing, Sovereignty, and Relational Justice in Higher Education (Table 8). SIG-Critical Educators for Social Justice; Roundtable Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Becoming Unshackled: A Reflective Inquiry into Healing, Sovereignty, and Relational Abolitionist Being Through Course Evaluations. *Nermin Vehabovic, Elon University*

Beyond Fairness to Whom: A Macro Distributive Justice Framework for University Scholarship Models. *TONG XIAO, Xiamen University*

Counter Mere Exposure: Animating Critical Dimensions of Intentionality and Transformation within a STEM-Medicine Program. *Janet Rocha, Arizona State University; Brian Cabral, University of Texas at Austin; Mara Lopez, Arizona State University*

The Role of Puente's Instructional Component in Student Success and Faculty Transformation of Their Practice. *Marisa E. Castellano, WestEd; Laura G. Lara-Brady, WestEd; Ravinder Singh, WestEd; Brenda Hernandez, WestEd; Ayanna Smith, WestEd*

The Identity Trap and the Reconstruction of Response Ethics In Higher Education. *xiaoyu qin, Xi An Univeristy of Technology*

30.050-9. Navigating Language, Identity, and Power (Table 9). SIG-Language and Social Processes; Roundtable Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Beyond the Code: Multilingual Fourth Graders' Metacognitive

Journeys Through Multimodal Texts. *Sabiha Sultana, University of California - Santa Barbara; Hui Zhang, University of Toledo; Valerie Meier, University of California - Santa Barbara*

"Because of My Research and Because I'm Latina": Intersectionalizing Identities in BIPOC Research Interviews. *Meghan Corella, University of British Columbia; Ryuko Kubota, University of British Columbia; Kyu Yun Lim, University of British Columbia; Rosa Dene David, University of British Columbia*

"I don't feel like I have to prove my identity by speaking only Spanish or only English.": Languaging as Identity Work Among Latinas at a PWI. *Stephanie Cuellar, Texas Christian University; Elsa Camargo, University of Texas - Arlington; Daniela Castro, Texas Christian University; Daisy Troche, Texas Christian University; Taryn Ozuna Allen, Texas Christian University; Maria Yareli Delgado, University of Texas - Arlington*

30.051. AERA Roundtable Session Thursday 7:45 am - Gold 4; Roundtable Session

30.051-1. Measurement Invariance and Differential Item Functioning in Educational Assessment (Table 1).

Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Auditing Item Fairness With AI-Simulated Personas: A DIF Analysis of the CES-D Scale. *Gengrui Zhang, University of Southern California*

Investigating Differential Item Functioning Across English and Indigenous Languages in South Africa Using PIRLS 2021 Data. *John Baffoe, University of Wisconsin-Milwaukee; Bo Zhang, University of Wisconsin - Milwaukee*

Investigating Intersectionality and Interactions in Differential Item Functioning: A Monte Carlo Simulation Study. *Winifred Wilberforce, The Ohio State University; Ann A. O'Connell, Rutgers University; Beverly J. Vandiver, The Ohio State University; Jerome V. D'Agostino, The Ohio State University*

Math Anxiety as a Source of Differential Item Functioning: Evidence from PISA 2022 Adaptive Testing. *Ergul Demir, Ankara University*

Measurement Invariance of Teaching Motivation across Public and Non-Public Experimental Schools in Taiwan. *Shao Hung Hsieh, National Chengchi University*

Chair: *Youn Seon Lim, University of Cincinnati*

30.051-2. Designing Inclusive and Human-Centered Technology for Learning (Table 2). Division C - Learning and Instruction; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;

7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Demographic Factors and Equity in AI-Supported Learning: A Mixed-Methods Study of Chatbot Use in MOOCs. *Songhee Han, Florida State University; Min Liu, University of Texas at Austin*

Examining Factors Influencing the Teachers' AIoT Technology Integration Quality through the COM-B Model and ICAP Framework. *Shuo Feng, Shanghai Jiao Tong University; Xin Gao, Shanghai Jiao Tong University; Qianqian Liu, Laoshan District Education Development Research Center, Qingdao; Zezhi Zhang, Digital Education Research Center of Laoshan District Education and Sports Bureau, Qingdao; Mingjie Li, Shibe District Education Research and Development Center, Qingdao; QiYu Zhang, Shandong Normal University; Yingbin Zhang, South China Normal University; Shuai Wang, Shanghai Jiao Tong University*

Integrating AI-Supported Cognitive Scaffolds in Secondary English Language Development Classrooms. *Kavita Rao, University of Hawai'i at Mānoa; Jonah Nakaza-Koizumi, University of Hawaii - Manoa; Sara Cothren Cook, University of Hawaii - Manoa; Christopher Ferry, Mid-Pacific; Jon Pennington, Mid-Pacific*

Supporting Historically Minoritized Youth's Computational Literacy Through Culturally-Relevant and Interdisciplinary Making and Wearable Learning Activities. *Gabriela T. Richard, University of Massachusetts - Amherst; Yanping Xu, Pennsylvania State University; Lillyanna Faimon, Pennsylvania State University; Heather Toomey Zimmerman, Pennsylvania State University; Jennifer L. Weible, Central Michigan University*

Teacher Perceptions and Equity in Virtual K-8 Education: A Critical Examination of Ability-Based Bias in Online Learning Environments. *Danielle Nicole Cunningham, Durham Public Schools*

Chair: *Joshua Littenberg-Tobias, GBH*

30.051-3. Method as Relational Disruption: Dialogue, Refusal, and Emergence in Qualitative Inquiry (Table 3).

Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Composting Harm, Cultivating Flourishing: Reflective Dialogue as the Soil of Just Educational Renewal. *Tiffany Lee Smith Tovey, University of North Carolina - Greensboro; Hannah Johnson, University of North Carolina - Greensboro; Stacy R. Huff, University of North Carolina - Greensboro*

Crocheting Refusal: Rhizomatic Pedagogies, Assemblages and Autopoietic Overturns. *Mariam Parvez Sheikh, University of Massachusetts - Amherst; Shruti Sheshadri, University of San Francisco*

Unexpected Moments in Qualitative Interviews: Potential and Possibilities When Navigating the Unexpected and Challenging in Interviewing. *Stephanie Anne Shelton, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Sun Gu, University of Alabama; April M. Jones, University of Montevallo*

Chair: *Stephanie Anne Shelton, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*

30.051-4. Transforming Systems: Reclaiming Knowledge and Practice for Collective Well-Being (Table 4). SIG-Cultural-Historical Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Quality of Life in Educational Institutions: Cultural-Historical Activity Theory as a Transformative Framework. *Mohammed Alzahrani, King Abdulaziz University*

Quantum Human Computing Power Fueling Systemic Transformation within a School-University-Tribal Nation Partnership. *Linda Orie, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Aydin Bal, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Dian Mawene, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Morgan Mayer-Jochimsen, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Reimagining Backwards and Reflecting Forward: How Black and Indigenous Practices Expand Researchers' Dialogic Reflexivity. *Paige A Hicks, Loyola University Chicago*

Sustainability In Precarity: Reframing Environmental Education As Collective Struggles. *Eliana Mercedes Bussi, University of Girona; Monica Lemos, Colégio Rio Branco; Alfredo Jornet Gil, Universitat de Girona*

Chair: *Jill M Sullivan, Arizona State University*

Discussant: *James Wright, Temple University*

30.051-5. From Data to Understanding: Building Fair and Rigorous Math and Science Assessments (Table 5). Division H - Research, Evaluation and Assessment in Schools; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Designing for Equity: Investigating the Process and Priorities in Revising Culturally Responsive Math Assessments. *Jennifer Aracely Rodriguez, University of Michigan Ann Arbor; Juan Ramon Sevilla, University of Illinois at Chicago; Alexandra Klyachkina, Chicago Public Schools*

Cognitive Complexity and Aspects of Rigor of Accountability Assessment Items. *Patrick Obot, University of Houston; Mandana Delavari, University of Houston; Arpana Manjunath, University of Houston; Jennifer B. Chauvot, University of Houston*

Unpacking Early Mathematical Cognition: A Joint Modeling of Speed and Accuracy Using Nested IRTree Models. *Xiao Chen Xu, University of California - Davis; Tony Albano,*

University of California - Davis

The Relationship between Formative Assessment Series of Tests (FAST) and National Assessment Test Results (NAFS). *Iman Al-Ruwaithi, Education and Training Evaluation Commission; Ioannis Tsaousis; Nasser Alresaini, Education and Training Evaluation Commission*

Chair: *Jennifer Aracely Rodriguez, University of Michigan Ann Arbor*

30.051-6. Encounters with Method: Narrative, Decolonial, and Diffraction Reorientations (Table 6). SIG-Qualitative Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

A Dialogic Approach to Unlearning in the Academy: Critical Iterative Duoethnography. *Christina L. Dobbs, Boston University; Christine Montecillo Leider, University of Massachusetts - Lowell*

Dissing Time, Disabling Narrative. *Srikala Narayan, Teachers College, Columbia University; Maria S. Guarino, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Re-turning to the Literature: Thinking with Diffraction Differently. *Katherine Ayers, St. Jude Children's Research Hospital; Susan N. Nordstrom, University of Alabama*

Chair: *Oona Fontanella-Nothom, California State University - Dominguez Hills*

30.051-7. Measurement Complexity in SEM: Cross-Loading, Invariance, and Heterogeneity (Table 7). SIG-Structural Equation Modeling and Multilevel Modeling Methods; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Detecting Cross-Loadings in CFA Using Bayesian Estimation: A Monte Carlo Simulation. *Tiejun Zhang, University of South Carolina; Ruiqin Gao, University of South Carolina; Xiaobo Wei, University of South Carolina; Jingtong Dou*

Emotional Problem Trajectories and Predictors in Adolescence: Using Latent Class Growth Analysis and SEM Forests. *Eunah Jang, Chungnam National University; Hyewon Chung, Chungnam National University*

Measurement Invariance and Sensitivity of Delta Fit Indexes in Non-Normal Data: A Monte Carlo Simulation Study. *Meixi Yu, University of Central Florida; Stephen A. Sivo, University of Central Florida; Parul Acharya, Columbus State University*

Rethinking Invariance: A Monte Carlo Evaluation of Critical Structural Equation Modeling. *Zachary K. Collier, University of Connecticut; Joshua Sukumar, University of Connecticut; Kirsten Reyna, University of Connecticut; Nicholas S. Bell, University of Connecticut; Veronica Velez, Western Washington University*

Chairs: *Chi-Ning Chang, Virginia Commonwealth University; Tzu-Wei Wang, Virginia Commonwealth University*

30.051-8. Critically Exploring Children’s Literature, Cultural Identities, and Languages (Table 8). SIG-Literature;

Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

“Becoming Raced:” A Critical Examination of Children’s Picture Books about Race. *Jen Bradley, Swarthmore College; Barbara Thelamour, Swarthmore College; Ryan Lei, Haverford College in Pennsylvania; Carolin Obispo, Swarthmore College; Nzana Thillot, Swarthmore College; Kylie Williams, Swarthmore College*

Exploring Korean Language Use in Korean American Children’s and Adolescent Literature. *Prisca Kim, University of New Mexico; Yoo Kyung Sung, University of New Mexico*

Rethinking and Reconstructing Community-Based Literary Spaces: A Case Study of Transnational Korean Mothers’ Book Club. *Yoo Kyung Sung, University of New Mexico; Eunjee Jang, University of Wisconsin - River Falls*

30.051-9. Black Women, Labor, and Leadership in College Athletics (Table 9). SIG-Research Focus on Education and Sport; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

“Am I Gonna Lose Myself?”: Stories of Weathering and Ontological Reclamation Among Black Women Professionals in Division I College Athletics. *Ezime Ofoegbu, Santa Clara University; Shaunté Yvette Hill, Santa Clara University*

From Recruitment to Disposability: Mapping the Temporal and Educational Pathways of Black Women in Division I Basketball. *Iman Lathan, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

How did we get here, cause nobody is supposed to be here. *Laetitia Adelson, University of Georgia*

Life After the Playing Field: Understanding the Postgraduate Career Transitions of Black Women College Athletes. *Briana Savage, University of California - Riverside*

Division and SIG Posters

30.052. AERA Poster Session Thursday 7:45am; Poster Session

30.052-1. Professional Learning and Instruction in Mathematics Education. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Poster Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall -

Exhibit Hall A; 7:45-9:15am

Posters:

1. Advancing Professional Development for K–12 Math Educators: Meta-Analysis of Effects, Challenges, and Next Steps (Poster 1). *Hyesun You, University of Iowa; Sunyoung Park, California Lutheran University; Li Zhu, University of Iowa; Dae S. Hong, University of Iowa; Minju Hong, Chung-Ang University*
2. Diffusing Mathematics Practitioner Articles via Social Media and Translational Visual Abstracts: A Randomized Controlled Trial (Poster 2). *Jessica Rodrigues, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Joel R. Malin, Miami University (OH); Elizabeth N. Farley-Ripple, University of Delaware; Joshua Rosenberg, University of Tennessee; Bret Staudt Willet, Florida State University; Emily Singell, University of Missouri*
3. Direct Instructions on a Math Task is Efficient, but Restricts Creativity of Some Elementary Students (Poster 3). *Andrea K Wikle, University of Georgia; Michael M. Barger, University of Georgia; Shannon Clark, University of Georgia*
4. Generative AI as a Tutor in Mathematical Problem-Solving: A Qualitative Study (Poster 4). *Bright Yeboah, University of Texas - El Paso; Kien H. Lim, The University of Texas - El Paso*
5. How do elementary mathematics teachers apply Bloom’s Taxonomy when designing digitally enhanced instructional activities? (Poster 5). *Catalina Lomos, Luxembourg Institute of Socio – Economic Research; S. Tell, Utrecht University*
6. Classroom Artifacts: Testing a Framework for Analyzing Quality Task Design in Mathematics (Poster 6). *Micaela Maria Bonilla, Stanford University; Maria Araceli Ruiz-Primo, Stanford University*

30.052-2. Poster Session: Statistical Theory, Quantitative Methods and Applications. Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Poster Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall -

Exhibit Hall A; 7:45-9:15am

Posters:

7. Specifying Weakly Informative Priors in Bayesian Meta-Analysis (Poster 7). *Junok Kim, University of California - Los Angeles; Michael H. Seltzer, University of California - Los Angeles*
8. Home Possessions and Student Achievement in the United States: Insights from PISA 2022 (Poster 8). *Latif Kadir, The Ohio State University; Valerie Ofori Aboah, The Ohio State University*
9. Predicting Instructional Quality in Elementary Math Classrooms Using Machine Learning and Observation Data (Poster 9). *Jerry Nelluvelil, Harvard University; Yixuan Cui, Harvard University*
10. An Application of Composite-Based Structural Equation Modeling to Instructional Coaching (Poster 10). *Marah*

Lambert, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Kyle T. Cox, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Carl Westine, University of North Carolina - Charlotte

11. Machine Learning in Predicting Undergraduate Student Attrition: A Scoping Review (Poster 11). *Oluwaseun Peter Farotimi, University of Tennessee; Oluwasayo Farotimi, Georgia Southern University; Comfort Happiness Omonkhodion, University of Central Florida; Funke Anuoluwapo Dada, Georgia Southern University; Debbie L. Hahs-Vaughn, University of Central Florida; Haiyan Bai, University of Central Florida*
12. New Tools, Old Questions: Rethinking Success in Gateway Statistics Courses through Machine Learning and Theory (Poster 12). *Sunny Nguyet Le, California State University - Fullerton*
13. ICT use and student achievement: Evidence from PIRLS 2021 using machine learning techniques (Poster 13). *Jose Manuel Cordero, Universidad de Extremadura; Víctor España, Universidad Miguel Hernández; María Gil-Izquierdo, Universidad Autónoma de Madrid; Lucia Mateos-Romero, Universidad de Extremadura*
14. Advancing Predictive Modeling in Behavioral Health with Gradient-Boosted Bootstrap Modeling (Poster 14). *Graham Zulu, University of Denver*

30.052-3. Building Just and Equitable Education Systems.

Division G - Social Context of Education; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall -
Exhibit Hall A; 7:45-9:15am

Posters:

15. Cannabis and Class: Social Class Discrimination and Cannabis Use Among Latine Adolescents (Poster 15). *Jeremiah Sabale, San Francisco State University; Jo Nisa Cabilogan, San Francisco State University; Abraham Tou Jang Moua, San Francisco State University; Manuel Abundis-Morales, San Francisco State University; Adam Suri, San Francisco State University; Busra Dogru, San Francisco State University; Jay Espinoza, San Francisco State University; Dania Smith, San Francisco State University; Bingyue Tan, San Francisco State University; Dolci Winer, University of San Francisco; Stella Sears-Bicknell, Oberlin College; Felicia Deshon, University of California - Los Angeles; Zena R. Mello, San Francisco State University*
16. Digital Silences: Intersectional Harms in Youth Online Life (Poster 16). *Chien-Chung Hsu, National Taichung University of Education; Yi-Ping Lo, Chinese Culture University*
17. Digital Wounds, Institutional Silence: Navigating Mistrust and Inaction in Taiwanese High Schools (Poster 17). *Yi-Ping Lo, Chinese Culture University; Chien-Chung Hsu, National Taichung University of Education*
18. Inclusive Postsecondary Education for Individuals with Intellectual Disabilities at Historically Black Colleges and

Universities (Poster 18). *Derrick Wesley, A Better Place Initiative LLC*

19. 'It's Okay Not To Be Okay': Reconceptualizing Mental Health Through A Black Transnational Collegians' Lens (Poster 19). *Patricia Feraud-King, College of the Holy Cross*
20. Justice Beyond Access: Epistemic and Pedagogical Dimensions of a MOOC-Based Model in Teacher Education (Poster 20). *MELEK NEŞE ÖZEFE, MEF University; Bengi Birgili Karabulut, MEF University*
21. Not One-Size-Fits-All: Variations in Parental Academic Socialization Across Race and Caregiver Identity (Poster 21). *Aniyah Davis-Hilton, University of Maryland - Baltimore County; Besjane Krasniqi, University of Maryland - Baltimore County; Susan Sonnenschein, University of Maryland - Baltimore County*
22. Potentials of Growing Up in Non-Academic Families for Coping with the Challenges of Doctoral Studies from the Perspective of First-Generation Academics (Poster 22). *Stephan Otto, IU Internationale Hochschule*
23. Props, personas, and PhDs: A duoethnographic drama of navigating whiteness in academia (Poster 23). *Cristie Suzukawa Clancy, Chapman University; Cristal B. Flores, Chapman University*
24. Racial Socialization, Gender, and Perceived Discrimination Among High-Achieving Black Youth (Poster 24). *Brandi Hilliard, The Ohio State University; Imani Reynolds, The Ohio State University; Rayna Hutcherson, The Ohio State University; Yusuf Hassan, The Ohio State University*
25. Reframing the Locus of the Problem: High-Masking Autistic Students and Higher Education (Poster 25). *Jamie Alain Smith Levitan, University of Maryland*
26. Shaped by Belief: Gendered Perceptions of Parental Beliefs Across Development (Poster 26). *Besjane Krasniqi, University of Maryland - Baltimore County; Aniyah Davis-Hilton, University of Maryland - Baltimore County; Diane Placide, University of Maryland - Baltimore County; Susan Sonnenschein, University of Maryland - Baltimore County*
27. Being Multiracial in a Monoracial Society (Poster 27). *Crystal Hutchinson, Rowan University; Shelley Zion, Rowan University; Jordana Simmons Berwise, Rowan University*
28. Breaking Barriers or Reinforcing Them? A Meta-Synthesis of Mentorship Experiences Among Underrepresented STEM Undergraduates (Poster 28). *Diana Beltran, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Shanika Wickramarachchi, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Claudia Luu, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Rachael Robnett, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*

30.052-4. zzzCancelled due to Withdrawals per 2-18-26 Chinese American Multilingual Students' Journey Through Graphic Novels.

Division G - Social Context of Education;
Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall -

Exhibit Hall A; 7:45-9:15am

30.052-5. Liberatory Evaluation Practices: Utilization, Identity, and Community in Educational Research.

Division H - Research, Evaluation and Assessment in Schools; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 7:45-9:15am

Posters:

29. Fostering Use: A Case Study of Evaluation Utilization in a Multi-Site STEM Program (Poster 29). *Courtney Stone, Arizona State University; Rachel Hogan, Arizona State University; Jessica Lopez, Arizona State University; Ayesha Boyce, Arizona State University; Caroline Long, University of Washington - Seattle; Christopher Arnette, University of Washington*
30. Futuring Through Plática: Graduate Student Dialogues on Identity, Practice, and Possibility in Evaluation (Poster 30). *Ashley Coughlin, Arizona State University; Mohammed Ibrahim, Arizona State University; Blessing Akinrotimi, Washington State University; Sandra Nabulega, Arizona State University; Ayesha Boyce, Arizona State University*

30.052-6. Global Metrics, Local Resistance: Education Policy, Technology, and the Politics of Learning.

Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 7:45-9:15am

Posters:

31. A Contemporary Map of Educational Knowledge Borrowing/Transfer: What is New? (Poster 31). *Ngoc Kim Tuyen Pham, Texas Tech University; Jeasik Cho, Texas Tech University; Romario Montaña-Ramos, Texas Tech University*
32. A PISA the Puzzle: Effects of the Establishment of the Programme for International Student Assessment on Education Reform (Poster 32). *Marcia Yang, Stanford University; Sofia Wilson, Stanford University; Patricia Bromley, Stanford University; Sean F. Reardon, Stanford University*
33. Investigating the Role of Privacy Concerns in the Use of Generative AI: A Moderated Double Mediation Effect among Arts Students in Chinese Universities (Poster 33). *Yating Wang, Beijing Normal-Hong Kong Baptist University; Yi Ronald Ding, Beijing Normal-Hong Kong Baptist University*
34. Less For Students, More For Teachers: Role Stress, Burnout, And Satisfaction Under China's Double-Reduction Policy (Poster 34). *Pengyu Lin, Wenzhou-Kean University; Jingyu Ma, Wenzhou-Kean University; Qingqing Zhou, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Jiayue Zhang, Wenzhou-Kean University; Qian Li, Wenzhou-Kean University*
35. Sidelined: How Policy Debates Shaped Trans Students'

Sports Involvement and Physical Activity Trends in Wisconsin (Poster 35). *Erin Gill, University of Pennsylvania; Benjamin Lebovitz, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Mollie McQuillan, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

36. The discursive uses of PISA results: What can they tell us about ideas of development? (Poster 36). *Alicia Rocio Elias-Caballero, Teachers College, Columbia University*
37. Organizational Functions of Teacher Preparation Programs at Minority-Serving Institutions (Poster 37). *Lillie Ko-Wong, University of California - San Diego*

30.052-7. AI, Learning, and Innovation: Emerging Research in Education.

SIG-Computer and Internet Application in Education; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 7:45-9:15am

Posters:

38. AI-Based Digital Textbooks, Mathematics, and Computational Thinking (Poster 38). *Bung Woo Jun, Florida State University; Seungki Shin, Seoul National University of Education; Dabin Park, Indiana University*
39. A Research of Corpus-based Medical Humanistic Emotional Vocabulary Analysis (Poster 39). *Xinyi Xie, New York University*
40. ChatGPT as a multilingual/multicultural tutor for adolescent and adult English learners (Poster 40). *Rebecca Curinga, College of Staten Island; Matthew X. Curinga, Adelphi University; Aaron Chia Yuan Hung, Adelphi University*
41. Computer-Based Assessment in Support of Productive Learner-Centered Error-Correction: What It Entails and Its Educational Potential (Poster 41). *Fu-Yun Yu, National Cheng Kung University*
42. Designing ChatGPT-Mediated Feedback Activities in EFL Writing: A Design-Based Study of the Dialogic Feedback Triangle (Poster 42). *YUNAN ZHANG, University of Hong Kong; Yongcan Liu, University of Cambridge*
43. Development of an AI-Transparency Rubric for K-12 Education (Poster 43). *Deepti Tagare, University of Texas - San Antonio; Hyejeong Lee, University of Texas - San Antonio*
44. Examining Human-LLM Interactions in Computational Thinking Empirical Studies: Insights from a Systematic Review (Poster 44). *Yimei Zhang, McGill University; Yajie Song, McGill University; Doina Precup, McGill University; Reihaneh Rabbany, McGill University; Maria Cutumisu, McGill University*
45. Exploring the Relationships between SRL and Design Behaviors in a Computer-Assisted Engineering Design Learning Environment (Poster 45). *Jacqueline Tan, Western Washington University; Juan Zheng, Lehigh University; Hanxiang Du, Western Washington University*
46. I am Interested in AI: A Systematic Review About AI Interest From 2010 To 2024 (Poster 46). *Woorin Hwang,*

University of Florida; Gabriella Haire, University of Florida; Pasha Antonenko, University of Florida

47. Let's talk about genAI: genAI-dentity Conversations in Education (Poster 47). *Lydia K Scholle-Cotton, Queen's University; Cheryl Lee-Yow, Queen's University - Kingston; Emily Luo, Queen's University - Kingston; Saad Chahine, Queen's University - Kingston*
48. Students' Strategy Use in Online Social Annotation: A Systematic Review (Poster 48). *Jieting Jerry Xin, The University of Hong Kong; Yingqi Chloe Wu, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Nicole J. Tavares, University of Hong Kong*
49. Validating a Survey Instrument to Measure Self-Regulated Learning in Asynchronous Online Discussions (Poster 49). *Jiarui Xie, The Ohio State University; Ana-Paula Correia, The Ohio State University*
50. Varying Modes of ChatGPT Integration: Effects on EFL Writing, Affective Responses, and Perceptions of LLMs (Poster 50). *Yiming Zhu, Texas A&M University; Hector H. Rivera, Texas A&M University; Heesun Chang, Texas A&M University; Zhoujing Lin, Liaoning Normal University; Eun Hye Grace Ko, Texas A&M University; Shuheng Li, East China Normal University*
51. What Draws the Upvotes? Examining Relationships among Performance, Interpersonal Skills, and Learning Behaviors in Online Social Annotation Environments (Poster 51). *Hanxiang Du, Western Washington University; Jiyoung Cheong, Western Washington University; Gaoxia Zhu, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University; Xiaoshan Huang, McGill University; Juan Zheng, Lehigh University; Tianlong Zhong, Nanyang Technological University; Chenyu Hou, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University; Shan Li, Lehigh University*
52. AI Competency and the Integration of AI in Learning: Views of University Master Students (Poster 52). *Chang Zhu, Vrije Universiteit Brussel*

30.053. e-Lightning Ed-Talk Session 6 - Stage 1. AERA e-Lightning Ed-Talks; AERA Ed Talk
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Exhibit Hall A - Stage 1; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

- How do elementary mathematics teachers apply Bloom's Taxonomy when designing digitally enhanced instructional activities? (Stage 1, 7:50 AM). *Catalina Lomos, Luxembourg Institute of Socio – Economic Research; S. Telli, Utrecht University*
- Classroom Artifacts: Testing a Framework for Analyzing Quality Task Design in Mathematics (Stage 1, 7:59 AM). *Micaela Maria Bonilla, Stanford University; Maria Araceli Ruiz-Primo, Stanford University*
- Diffusing Mathematics Practitioner Articles via Social Media and Translational Visual Abstracts: A Randomized

Controlled Trial (Stage 1, 8:08 AM). *Jessica Rodrigues, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Joel R. Malin, Miami University (OH); Elizabeth N. Farley-Ripple, University of Delaware; Joshua Rosenberg, University of Tennessee; Bret Staudt Willet, Florida State University; Emily Singell, University of Missouri*

Generative AI as a Tutor in Mathematical Problem-Solving: A Qualitative Study (Stage 1, 8:17 AM). *Bright Yeboah, University of Texas - El Paso; Kien H. Lim, The University of Texas - El Paso*

Machine Learning in Predicting Undergraduate Student Attrition: A Scoping Review (Stage 1, 8:26 AM). *Oluwaseun Peter Farotimi, University of Tennessee; Oluwasayo Farotimi, Georgia Southern University; Comfort Happiness Omonkhodion, University of Central Florida; Funke Anuoluwapo Dada, Georgia Southern University; Debbie L. Hahs-Vaughn, University of Central Florida; Haiyan Bai, University of Central Florida*

Advancing Predictive Modeling in Behavioral Health with Gradient-Boosted Bootstrap Modeling (Stage 1, 8:35 AM). *Graham Zulu, University of Denver*

Predicting Instructional Quality in Elementary Math Classrooms Using Machine Learning and Observation Data (Stage 1, 8:44 AM). *Jerry Nelluvelil, Harvard University; Yixuan Cui, Harvard University*

New Tools, Old Questions: Rethinking Success in Gateway Statistics Courses through Machine Learning and Theory (Stage 1, 8:53 AM). *Sunny Nguyet Le, California State University - Fullerton*

Chair: *Vaughn W.M. Watson, Michigan State University*

30.054. e-Lightning Ed-Talk Session 6 - Stage 2. AERA e-Lightning Ed-Talks; AERA Ed Talk
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Exhibit Hall A - Stage 2; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

- Cannabis and Class: Social Class Discrimination and Cannabis Use Among Latine Adolescents (Stage 2, 7:50 AM). *Jeremiah Sabale, San Francisco State University; Jo Nisa Cabilogan, San Francisco State University; Abraham Tou Jang Moua, San Francisco State University; Manuel Abundis-Morales, San Francisco State University; Adam Suri, San Francisco State University; Busra Dogru, San Francisco State University; Jay Espinoza, San Francisco State University; Dania Smith, San Francisco State University; Bingyue Tan, San Francisco State University; Dolci Winer, University of San Francisco; Stella Sears-Bicknell, Oberlin College; Felicia Deshon, University of California - Los Angeles; Zena R. Mello, San Francisco State University*
- Inclusive Postsecondary Education for Individuals with Intellectual Disabilities at Historically Black Colleges and Universities (Stage 2, 7:59 AM). *Derrick Wesley, A Better Place Initiative LLC*

'It's Okay Not To Be Okay': Reconceptualizing Mental Health Through A Black Transnational Collegians' Lens (Stage 2, 8:08 AM). *Patricia Feraud-King, College of the Holy Cross*

Potentials of Growing Up in Non-Academic Families for Coping with the Challenges of Doctoral Studies from the Perspective of First-Generation Academics (Stage 2, 8:17 AM). *Stephan Otto, IU Internationale Hochschule*

Props, personas, and PhDs: A duoethnographic drama of navigating whiteness in academia (Stage 2, 8:26 AM). *Cristie Suzukawa Clancy, Chapman University; Cristal B. Flores, Chapman University*

Shaped by Belief: Gendered Perceptions of Parental Beliefs Across Development (Stage 2, 8:35 AM). *Besjane Krasniqi, University of Maryland - Baltimore County; Aniyah Davis-Hilton, University of Maryland - Baltimore County; Diane Placide, University of Maryland - Baltimore County; Susan Sonnenschein, University of Maryland - Baltimore County*

Being Multiracial in a Monoracial Society (Stage 2, 8:44 AM). *Crystal Hutchinson, Rowan University; Shelley Zion, Rowan University; Jordana Simmons Berwise, Rowan University*

Chair: *Stephen D. Hancock, North Carolina A&T State University*

30.055. e-Lightning Ed-Talk Session 6 - Stage 3. AERA e-Lightning Ed-Talks; AERA Ed Talk
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Exhibit Hall A - Stage 3; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

The discursive uses of PISA results: What can they tell us about ideas of development? (Stage 3, 7:50 AM). *Alicia Rocio Elias-Caballero, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Less For Students, More For Teachers: Role Stress, Burnout, And Satisfaction Under China's Double-Reduction Policy (Stage 3, 7:59 AM). *Pengyu Lin, Wenzhou-Kean University; Jingyu Ma, Wenzhou-Kean University; Qingqing Zhou, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Jiayue Zhang, Wenzhou-Kean University; Qian Li, Wenzhou-Kean University*

A Contemporary Map of Educational Knowledge Borrowing/Transfer: What is New? (Stage 3, 8:08 AM). *Ngoc Kim Tuyen Pham, Texas Tech University; Jeasik Cho, Texas Tech University; Romario Montaña-Ramos, Texas Tech University*

ChatGPT as a multilingual/multicultural tutor for adolescent and adult English learners (Stage 3, 8:17 AM). *Rebecca Curinga, College of Staten Island; Matthew X. Curinga, Adelphi University; Aaron Chia Yuan Hung, Adelphi University*

Examining Human-LLM Interactions in Computational Thinking Empirical Studies: Insights from a Systematic Review (Stage 3, 8:26 AM). *Yimei Zhang, McGill University; Yajie Song, McGill University; Doina Precup, McGill University; Reihaneh Rabbany, McGill University; Maria Cutumisu, McGill University*

Let's talk about genAI: genAI-dentity Conversations in

Education (Stage 3, 8:35 AM). *Lydia K Scholle-Cotton, Queen's University; Cheryl Lee-Yow, Queen's University - Kingston; Emily Luo, Queen's University - Kingston; Saad Chahine, Queen's University - Kingston*

Validating a Survey Instrument to Measure Self-Regulated Learning in Asynchronous Online Discussions (Stage 3, 8:44 AM). *Jiarui Xie, The Ohio State University; Ana-Paula Correia, The Ohio State University*

Varying Modes of ChatGPT Integration: Effects on EFL Writing, Affective Responses, and Perceptions of LLMs (Stage 3, 8:53 AM). *Yiming Zhu, Texas A&M University; Hector H. Rivera, Texas A&M University; Heesun Chang, Texas A&M University; Zhoujing Lin, Liaoning Normal University; Eun Hye Grace Ko, Texas A&M University; Shuheng Li, East China Normal University*

Thursday, April 9th, 8:00 am

31.010. University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign College Partner Research Collaboration. Affiliated Groups; Seminar
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, San Fernando; 8:00-11:00am

Thursday, April 9th, 8:30 am

SIG Sessions

32.010. School Site Visit to Detracking School – Da Vinci Schools. SIG-Access, Detracking, and Tracking
Cosponsored with Spotlight on Los Angeles and the Region; Off-Site Visit
Da Vinci Schools, Advance Registration Required – Meet outside the Crypto Arena at the corner of 12th Street East and Gilbert Lindsay Drive; 8:30am to 1:00pm
Chair: *Constance Clark, Rutgers University - Newark*

32.011. Journal for the Education of the Gifted Editorial Board Meeting. Affiliated Groups; Board Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Level 3, Santa Monica D; 8:30-9:30am

Thursday, April 9th, 9:00 am

AERA Related Activities

33.010. AERA Research Engagement and Development With Youth (READY) Program Session 2 (Invitation Only).
AERA Related Activities; Invited Roundtable

Los Angeles Convention Center, Room 306AB; 9:00am to 8:00pm

Chair: *Lori Diane Hill, American Educational Research Association*

Thursday, April 9th, 9:45 am

Governance Meetings and Events

34.001. AERA Committee on Scholars and Advocates for Gender Equity in Education (SAGE). AERA Governance; Governance Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 514; 9:45-11:15am

Chair: *Francesca López, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

34.002. AERA Fellows Committee Meeting: Closed Meeting.

AERA Governance; Governance Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum D; 9:45-11:15am

Chair: *Kara S. Finnigan, University of Michigan*

34.003. American Educational Research Journal: Closed Editorial Board Meeting. AERA Governance; Governance Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 518; 9:45-11:15am

Chair: *John Neikirk, American Educational Research Association*

Presidential Sessions

34.010. How the Science of Learning and Development and the Neurosciences Can Inform Re-Envisioning Human Possibility. AERA Presidential Session; Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 408A; 9:45-11:15am

Chair: *Carol D. Lee, Northwestern University*

Presenters: *Mary Helen Immordino-Yang, University of Southern California; Megan Bang, Northwestern University; Carol D. Lee, Northwestern University; Barbara Rogoff, University of California - Santa Cruz; Cati V. de los Rios, University of California - Berkeley*

Discussant: *Ezekiel J. Dixon-Roman, Teachers College, Columbia University*

34.011. Shifting the Paradigm: Leveraging Mentoring Networks to Advance Educational Research. AERA Presidential Session; Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 409AB; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

PAST: Unforgetting Mentoring Histories and Navigating Tensions. *Carol A. Mullen, Virginia Tech*

PRESENT: Mentoring Networks in Action. *Nora Dominguez, University of New Mexico*

FUTURE: Affirming Equitable Futures. *Kathleen Mary Cowin, Washington State University - Tri-Cities*

Chair: *Nora Dominguez, University of New Mexico*

AERA Research and Science Policy Sessions

34.012. Transforming the Special Education Workforce: Research and Complex Systems Perspectives – An AERA Publication. AERA Science and Policy Sessions; Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 403B; 9:45-11:15am

Chair: *Erica D. McCray, University of Florida*

Participants: *Marcia L. Rock, University of North Carolina - Greensboro; Lisa Dieker, University of Kansas*

Discussants: *Roddy Theobald, American Institutes for Research; Jason C. Chow, Vanderbilt University*

AERA Sessions

34.013. 2025 Early Career Award Lecture: Research at the Intersection of Law and Education Policy: Conditions, Strategies, and Mechanisms that Shape Educational Equity. AERA Sessions; Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 408B; 9:45-11:15am

Chair: *Bryan A. Brown, Stanford University*

Presenter: *Raquel Muñiz, Boston College*

Committee Sessions

34.014. Designing, Defending, and Sustaining Equity for Communities of Color in Politically Hostile Climates. Committee on Scholars of Color in Education; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 506; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Developing and Refining a Multimodal Intervention to Promote Latino Students Postsecondary Readiness. *Alejandra Garcia Isaza, University of Texas at Austin; Charles R. Martinez,*

University of Texas at Austin; John Mark Eddy, University of Texas at Austin; Diana Orozco-Lapray, University of Texas at Austin; Sarah Mason, University of Texas at Austin
Latino Male College Enrollment in the Wake of COVID-19: Revisiting Postsecondary Pathways Five Years Later. *Victor B. Sáenz, University of Texas at Austin; Luis Ponjuan, Texas A&M University; Rodrigo Aguayo, University of Texas at Austin*

Disrupting the Mechanisms of Equity Suppression in an Anti-“DEI” Policy Context: Lessons from A Case Study. *Liliana M. Garcés, University of Texas at Austin; Jackie Pedota, University of Texas at Austin; Eliza Epstein, University of Texas at Austin*

Chair: *John Mark Eddy, University of Texas at Austin*

Discussant: *Charles R. Martinez, University of Texas at Austin*

34.015. Division D Fireside Chat: From Ivory Tower to Public Square: Sharing Your Research Beyond Academia.

Graduate Student Council Cosponsored with Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 402A; 9:45-11:15am

Chair: *Yitong Yue, University of Virginia*

Panelists: *Yasmiyn Irizarry, University of Texas at Austin; Jamila Lyiscott, University of Massachusetts - Amherst*

34.016. Reframing Global Education: Internationalization and Transnational Perspectives.

International Relations Committee; Paper Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 502A; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

The Future of Work: Teach For All’s Global Vision for Education. *Arianna Marie Rodriguez, University of California - Santa Cruz*

Reading Between the Lines: Framing Internationalization in U.S. University Statements. *Elena Broscritto, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Teaching Across Borders: Responsible Well-being Among Transnational Educators in the U.S. and China. *Shuang Fu, New York University; Yixuan Wang, Gwinnett County Public Schools*

The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development and SDG4: Global Progress, Challenges and Countermeasures Faced by China. *yihong jiao, Beijing Normal University*

34.017. Resisting Educational Abandonment in Los Angeles: Recovering a Critical History of Activism in Williams.

Social Justice Action Committee; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 501C; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

The Hammer and Nails: Re-Constructing LA Schools After the

Uprising. *Esa Syeed, California State University - Long Beach*

Unforgetting History of Agency and Resistance: Fremont Students and Parents Take Action Against State-Sanctioned Discrimination. *Diana A. Porras, California State University - Long Beach*

Examining Educators’ & Administrators’ Role in the Williams Case: A Case Study of Fremont High. *Lluliana Alonso, California State University - Long Beach*

Chair: *Oscar Navarro, California State University - Long Beach*
Discussant: *Oscar Navarro, California State University - Long Beach*

International Organization Sessions

34.018. Envisioning Creative and Inclusive Educational Futures: Perspectives from the Educational Studies Association of Ireland (ESAI) in its Fiftieth Year.

International Aligned Organizations/Educational Studies Association of Ireland - ESAI; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum B; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Historical Legacies and Future Possibilities: Exploring Sexuality Education through Communities of Practice in Ireland. *Suzanne O’Keeffe, Maynooth University; Elva Casey, Maynooth University*

Considering historical erasures and persistent normative assumptions: Researching the lived experiences of autistic academics working in autism friendly universities. *Maggie Green, Atlantic Technological University*

From Probation to Pedagogy: Reimagining Teacher Induction through Co-Teaching and Collaborative Action Research (CAR). *Ciara Uí Chonduibh, Scoil Naomh Fiach*

Designing Futures: Envisioning and Embedding 21st Century Education through Transformative Innovation in Learning, Teaching and Assessment. *Tony Hall, University of Galway*

Re-imagining initial teacher education in Ireland. *Teresa O’Doherty, Marino Institute of Education*

Chair: *Aman Yadav, Michigan State University*

Division Sessions

34.019. From Memory to Machine: Rethinking Curriculum in AI-Mediated Education.

Division B - Curriculum Studies; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304A; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

AI Literacy and Philosophical Research on Artificial Superintelligence: A Scoping Review and Synthesis. *Nicolas Jordan Tanchuk, University of Illinois at Urbana-*

Champaign; Rebecca M. Taylor, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Seunghyun Lee, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Ashish Gaur, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign

Artificial Intelligence and the Future of Curriculum. *Leonard J. Waks, Qufu Normal University, Shandong China*

Curricular Fallout: What the Cold War, COVID, and AI Have in Common. *Amanda M. Price, Southern Regional Technical College; John Wilson Gordon, Mercer University*

From Erasure to Futures: AI-Driven Curricula and the Politics of Memory in Emerging School Models. *Rick J. Voithofer, The Ohio State University*

You Can Find Me in the Cloud: How Digital Platformitization Controls Teaching. *Anne Shields, Bard High School Early College; Madhu Narayanan, Florida International University*

Discussant: *Zhaochen Gu, University of Illinois at Chicago*

34.020. Adaptation of Science Instructional Materials: Localizing Curriculum Materials to Support Equitable Sensemaking. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Symposium

Westin Bonaventure, Level 2, Echo Park; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Building Pedagogical Design Capacity through Conceptually Rich Professional Learning. *Mon-Lin Ko, University of Colorado - Boulder; Nga Hoang, University of Colorado - Boulder; Melissa R. Campanella, University of Colorado - Boulder; Kerri Wingert, Good Question Research & Evaluation*

Curriculum-based Professional Learning to Support Teachers in Customizing Curriculum for their Students and Context. *Katherine L. McNeill, Boston College; Austin Moore, Boston College; Maria A. Moreno Vera, Boston College; Brianna Balke, Boston College; Laura M. O'Dwyer, Boston College; Samuel Lee, California State University - Long Beach; Renee Affolter, OpenSciEd*

Supporting Productive Customization Of HQIM Through Assessment Task Design. *Abraham Lo, BSCS Science Learning; Elaine Klein, BSCS Science Learning; Melissa R. Campanella, University of Colorado - Boulder; William R. Penuel, University of Colorado - Boulder*

Outcomes From A Conference On Localizing High Quality Science Instructional Materials: Perspectives Across Educational Systems. *Suzanna J. Loper, University of California - Berkeley; Daniel Alcazar-Roman; Vanessa B. Lujan, University of California - Berkeley*

Chair: *Katherine L. McNeill, Boston College*

Discussant: *Tiffany Neill, University of Central Oklahoma*

34.021. Data Science as a Tool for Engaging in Civic Education. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Structured Poster Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 515A;

9:45-11:15am

Participants:

1. Navigating Personal and Sociopolitical Tensions in Students' Engagements with Food Access Data (Poster 1). *Kristin A. Searle, Utah State University; Deborah Fields, Utah State University; Mengying Jiang, Utah State University; Bolaji R Bamidele, Utah State University; Michaela Harper, Utah State University; Waqas Ahmad, Utah State University; Emma Griffin, Utah State University*

2. The Voice from Our Community: Appalachian Youth Crafting Data Visualizations for Social Good (Poster 2). *Yilang Zhao, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Lynn L. Hodge, University of Tennessee*

3. Analyzing Data for Local Non-profit Organizations (Poster 3). *Michelle Friend, University of Nebraska - Omaha; Betty N Love, University of Tennessee; Rebecca Brusky, University of Nebraska - Omaha; Andrew Swift, University of Nebraska - Omaha*

4. Using Data to Explore the Past, Examine the Present, and Envision the Future (Poster 4). *Traci Higgins, TERC; Kaylene Mae Stevens, Boston University; Kathryn Hobbs, TERC; Andee Rubin, TERC*

5. Open Inquiry on Open Government Data: A Data-Driven Approach in CS Education for Civic Engagement (Poster 5). *Sayed Mohsin Reza, Pennsylvania State University - Harrisburg*

6. Data Literacy as an Essential Component of Constructive Civic Engagement (Poster 6). *Jennifer D. Sayed, Southern Methodist University; Nick Okafor, trubel&co*

7. Datasets as Primary Sources to Engage in Civic Education in Middle School Social Studies Classrooms (Poster 7). *Katherine M. Miller, Concord Consortium; Trang C. Tran, University of Colorado - Boulder; Joseph L. Polman, University of Colorado - Boulder*

Chairs: *Katherine M. Miller, Concord Consortium; Traci Higgins, TERC*

Discussant: *Travis Weiland, University of North Carolina - Charlotte*

34.022. Intervening for Impact: Mindsets, Executive Function, and Self-Regulation from Early Childhood to College.

Division C - Learning and Instruction Cosponsored with SIG-Studying and Self-Regulated Learning; Paper Session Westin Bonaventure, Level 3, Avalon; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Effects of Growth Mindset Integrated Reading Intervention for Students with Reading Difficulties in Grades 4-5. *Eunsoo Cho, University of California - Riverside; Philip Capin, Harvard University; Sarah Reiley, Michigan State University*

Examination of the Impact of Students' Participation Patterns During a Semester-Long Self-Regulated Learning Intervention. *Rayne A. Sperling, Pennsylvania State University; SeongYeup Kim, Pennsylvania State University;*

Jennelle L. Malcos, Pennsylvania State University; Louis Leblond, Pennsylvania State University; Ying Wang, FHI 360

Executive Function, Math, and Reaction Time: Implications for Task Design and Intervention in Early Childhood. *Josh Medrano, University of California - Berkeley; Dana Miller-Cotto, University of California - Berkeley*

Possible Selves Interventions: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Tanner Reid Phillips, University of Rochester; Hunter Standish, University of California - Irvine; Kamalakannan SO M Vijayakumar, University of California - Irvine; Amy L. Dent, University of California - Irvine*

Supporting Student Agency in Undergraduate Biomedical Education: An Online Agentive Orientation Intervention. *Amanda Vite, University of Southern California; Keenan Pituch, Arizona State University; Carlton J. Fong, Texas State University; Germine Awad, University of Michigan; Yanyan Zong, University of Southern California; Pedram Zarei, Texas State University; Lillian Nguyen, University of Michigan; Diane Lee, University of Southern California; Christa Bancroft, University of Southern California; Kristy Daniel, Texas State University - San Marcos; Timothy A. McKay, University of Michigan; Stephen Aguilar; Kevin O'Neal Cokley, University of Michigan; Carolyn Jess, Texas State University; Erika A. Patall, University of Southern California*

Chair: *Amanda Vite, University of Southern California*

Discussant: *Cameron Hecht, University of Rochester*

34.023. Math for All: Math Games and Activities to Improve Learning and Attitudes Across Diverse Contexts.

Division C - Learning and Instruction; Symposium Westin Bonaventure, Level 2, Beverly; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Improving Math Attitudes with a Play-Based Intervention: Evidence from Kosovo. *Siling Guo, University of California - Irvine; Vanessa Bermudez, Loyola Marymount University; Eda Vula, University of Prishtina; Njomza Selimi, University of Ljubljana; Blerina Tafolli, University of Prishtina; Lindsey E. Richland, University of California - Irvine; Katherine T Rhodes, University of California - Irvine; Drew Bailey, University of California - Irvine; Andres Sebastian Bustamante, University of California - Irvine; Kreshnik Nasi Begolli, University of California - Irvine*

Improving Math Outcomes Through a Play-Based Intervention Adapted for an Indigenous Community in Mexico. *Andres Sebastian Bustamante, University of California - Irvine; Vanessa Noemy Bermudez, University of California - Irvine; Jesse Giovanni Sanchez, University of California - Irvine; TERESITA MERINO, University of California - Irvine; Hernan Encinas, University of California - Irvine; Kreshnik Nasi Begolli, University of California - Irvine; Drew Bailey, University of California - Irvine*

Effects of Playful Learning Activities on First Graders' Early

Fraction Knowledge. *Nancy C. Jordan, University of Delaware; Abigail Losey, University of Delaware; Alexandria Viegut, University of Wisconsin - Eau Claire; Christina Areizaga Barbieri, University of Delaware; Ilyse Resnick, University of Canberra; Nora Newcombe, Temple University*

Unpacking Professional Development Impact: Dosage, Implementation, and Student Outcomes in Early Math. *Caroline Brayer Ebby, University of Pennsylvania; Anahita Kumar, University of Pennsylvania; Karina Diaz, University of Pennsylvania*

Learning to Play: Novice Teachers' Experiences in Implementing a Play-Based Math Intervention. *Pritha Sengupta., University of California - Irvine; Leigh Allen, Wesleyan University; Ruby Seamon, Wesleyan University; Saige Rovero, Wesleyan University; Anna Shusterman, Wesleyan University*

Chair: *Siling Guo, University of California - Irvine*

Discussant: *Daniela Alvarez-Vargas, Colorado State University*

34.024. Navigating Identity, Equity, and Cultural Narratives in Education. Division E - Counseling and Human

Development; Paper Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 301B; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Elementary Schoolers' Intergroup Attitudes: The Intersection of Race/Ethnicity, Gender, Gender Expression and Social Class. *Negin Ghavami, Loyola Marymount University; Dzorgbenyui Adzo Gbagbo, Loyola Marymount University; Colson Lee, Loyola Marymount University; Ryan Anderson, Loyola Marymount University; Sandra Graham, University of California - Los Angeles*

"Because we're Hispanic, because we're Latinas": Avoiding Chicana/Latina Cultural Scripts. *Maritza E. Salazar, Mexican American Opportunity Foundation*

Do Latino and White Parents Interpret DECA's Behavioral Concerns in Similar Ways: Assessing Measurement Invariance. *Ji Eun Park, NORC at the University of Chicago; Vi-Nhuan Le, NORC at the University of Chicago; Diana Schaack, University of Colorado - Denver; Laura S. Hamilton, National Center for the Improvement of Educational Assessment, Inc.; Cristal Cisneros, Denver Preschool Program; Jolene Castillo Gregory, Denver Public Schools*

Moderating Role of Academic Major on Race-Related Stress and Performance in Black College Students. *Sydney A Defrietas, The College of New Jersey; Adaurennaya C. Onyewuanyi, The College of New Jersey*

Chair: *David Wakefield, California State University - Northridge*

Discussant: *Jessica Morales-Chicas, California State University - Los Angeles*

34.025. Preparing and Supporting School Counselors to Meet

Equity Challenges. Division E - Counseling and Human Development; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 406AB;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Exploring the lived experiences of school counselors' preparation in the career development of Black high school students. *Carla B. Cheatham, Seattle University; Renae D. Mayes, University of Arizona; Adrienne Robertson, Temple University; Betsy Marina Perez, California State University, Northridge*

Intersection of Disciplinary Practices, Mental Health, and Suicide Prevention for Black Youth: School Professionals' Perspectives. *Dana Griffin, Pennsylvania State University; Constance A. Lindsay, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Marisa Marraccini, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Jay Mathis, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Telieha Middleton, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*

School Counselors and the Multidimensional Identity Development of Black Male Student-Athletes. *Paul C. Harris, Virginia Commonwealth University*

There is Still Work to be Done: Advancing School Counselor Engineering Career Knowledge & Skills through Professional Learning Community. *Renae D. Mayes, University of Arizona; Medha Dalal, Arizona State University; Yijia Chen, University of Arizona; Lydia Ross, Arizona State University*

Counseling Complexities: School Counselors' Perceptions of Role Constraints, Student Support Needs and Counseling Practices. *Anita A. Young, Johns Hopkins University; Jodi L. Miller, Johns Hopkins University; Norma Day-Vines, Johns Hopkins University; Yiyang Xiong, Johns Hopkins University; Lieny Jeon, University of Virginia; Juliet Ray, Johns Hopkins University*

Chair: *Laura Owen, San Diego State University*

Discussant: *Laura Owen, San Diego State University*

34.026. Unforgetting Indigenous Education Histories to Cultivate Hwíl Haahodinééh: Diné Experiences in the Mormon Indian Placement Program. Division F - Historical Inquiry in Education Cosponsored with SIG-Indigenous Peoples of the Americas; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 504;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Non-Native Facilitator and Participant 1. *M. Nathan Tanner, University of Nevada - Reno*

Diné Participant 2. *Oliver G. Tapaha, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Diné Participant 3. *Raythina Tapaha-Yazzie, Many Farms Public School*

Diné Participant 4. *Priscilla Weaver, Dine College*

Diné Participant 5. *Randy Benally, University of New Mexico*

Chair: *Jennifer Johnson, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Discussant: *M. Nathan Tanner, University of Nevada - Reno*

34.027. Disrupting Deficit Logics: Centering Community Knowledge in the Design of Educational Research.

Division G - Social Context of Education; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 303A;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Envisioning an Àmà Approach in Community-engaged Research. *Vaughn W.M. Watson, Michigan State University; Sandra Boateng, Michigan State University; Dominic Hateka, Michigan State University; Akinkunmi Ibrahim Oseni, Michigan State University*

A Malverde approach to research: An analysis of the redistribution of labor and resources in a participatory design music study. *Yared Portillo, University of California - Berkeley*

Practicing a Moving Literacies Curriculum with Indigenous and Latinx Youth in a Migrant Education Program. *Christine Seon "Sol" Rheem, Michigan State University*

Composite Narratives as Method in Intergenerational Community-Based Research. *Guadalupe Barrientos, University of Pennsylvania; Jancarlos Montoya Mejia, University of Pennsylvania; Nelson Flores, University of Pennsylvania*

Chair: *Nelson Flores, University of Pennsylvania*

Discussant: *Limarys Caraballo, Teachers College, Columbia University*

34.028. Unlearning Failure: Black Scholars and the Promise of Educational Transformation in Global Contexts. Division

G - Social Context of Education; Workshop
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 301A;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Beyond the Mestiçagem: Black Students and Social Mobility Through Higher Education in Brazil. *Washington Galvao, University of Minnesota*

Schooling Against the Grain: Alternative Education as Ideological Resistance. *Bodunrin O. Banwo, University of Massachusetts - Boston; Ezekiel Joubert, California State University - Los Angeles; Kashmeel McKoena, University of Massachusetts - Boston*

Slam Poetry as Testimonio: How It Informs YPAR Practices in ES, Brazil. *Monyque Assis Suzano, University of Minnesota*

Chair: *Washington Galvao, University of Minnesota*

Presenters: *Monyque Assis Suzano, University of Minnesota; Bodunrin O. Banwo, University of Massachusetts - Boston; Ashley Watson, University of Minnesota*

Discussants: *Ezekiel Joubert, California State University - Los Angeles; Mirtes Santos, Universidade de Cabo Verde; Eliane Quintiliano Nascimento, University of Texas at Austin*

34.029. The State of Black Student Literacy Growth and Proficiency in Michigan: A Comprehensive Data Analysis. Division H - Research, Evaluation and Assessment in Schools; Symposium

InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 7th Floor, Hollywood Ballroom I; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

From Data Overload to Precision Teaching: Using Assessment to Inform Instruction. *Joe Musial, University of Michigan - Dearborn; Aaron Johnson, Archetype Consulting; Tera Shamey, Archetype Consulting*

Interrogating the Numbers: A Statistical Analysis of Growth, Equity, and Missed Signals. *Tera Shamey, Archetype Consulting*

Liberating Literacy: A CRI Framework for Reading Data on Black Children. *Aaron Johnson, Archetype Consulting*

Chair: *Neha Sobti, Hofstra University*

Discussant: *Alfred W. Tatum, Metropolitan State University of Denver*

34.030. Division I Mentoring Network Social. Division I - Education in the Professions; Reception

Westin Bonaventure, Level 3, Hollywood Ballroom; 9:45-11:15am

Chairs: *Sacha Sharp, Indiana University; Kadian McIntosh, University of Arizona; Francesca A. Williamson, University of Michigan*

Participants: *Peggy Gesing, Old Dominion University; Nicole Wang-Trexler, Vanguard Inc.; Xiaomei Song, Case Western Reserve University; Ramona Dorough, UT Southwestern Medical Center; Matthew Pearson, DePaul University; Elgloria A. Harrison, Lehman College - CUNY*

34.031. Guaranteed Income: Understanding Unconditional Cash and Partnerships For Educational Research with Community Colleges. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Symposium

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum G; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

LA BOOST: GI Implementation and Decision-Making. *Kelly King, Los Angeles Community College District; Katy Cisneros, Los Angeles Community College District*

Investing in the future of these students is to invest in the future of the community”: Emergent qualitative findings from the LACCD GI pilot project. *Briana Nichols, University of Pennsylvania; Monique Y. Perry, University of Pennsylvania*

Exploring Guaranteed Income and Student Well-being: Digital Storytelling from LA BOOST Community College Students. *Monique Y. Perry, University of Pennsylvania*

Disaster Relief: Supporting Community College Students during the 2025 LA Wildfires Crisis and Beyond. *Kelly King, Los Angeles Community College District; Katy*

Cisneros, Los Angeles Community College District; Andrea Terrones, California Youth Empowerment Commission

Chair: *Briana Nichols, University of Pennsylvania*

Discussant: *Kendrick B. Davis, University of Southern California*

34.032. Networks and Support Systems in Higher Education.

Division J - Postsecondary Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum F; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

“But What Happens After?”: The Value of Higher Education for Undocumented Students. *Emma Miriam Lezberg, Harvard University*

Clarifying Community: College Students’ Meaning-Making Through Community Cultural Wealth. *Hyun Kyoung Ro, Korea University; Lisa Delacruz Combs, University of North Texas*

How Do Undocumented College Students Engage in Their Campus Resource Ecosystem?: A Latent Profile Analysis. *Laura E. Enriquez, University of California - Irvine; Monica Cornejo, Cornell University*

Latine STEM College Students’ Support Network Properties: Descriptive Findings from a Three-Wave Panel Study.

Kyoungjin Jang-Tucci, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Nidia Bañuelos, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Ross J. Benbow, University of Wisconsin - Madison

The Socialization of STEM Postdoctoral Fellows at an Environmental Science Institute: an Interpretive Case Study. *Alexios Rosario-Moore, Northern Illinois University; Steven McGee, The Learning Partnership*

Discussant: *Cassandra Victoria Guzman, Cornell University*

34.033. Reimagining, Reframing and Resisting: Exploring Racial Inequity Within Our Institutions. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum H; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

The Power to Belong: A Radical Reimagining of Black Belonging through Collins’ Domains of Power. *Chino Ekwueme, University of Michigan*

Undergraduate Learning Assistants’ Conceptions of Racial Equity: Reproducing and Resisting Color-Evasiveness in Postsecondary STEM Classrooms. *Regan Levy, Michigan State University; Shahnaz Masani, Michigan State University*

Words That Win or Wither: How Message Framing and Ideology Beliefs Shape Campus Support for Racial Equity. *Royal M. Johnson, University of Southern California; Terrill O. Taylor, University of Maryland*

Rethinking Bias in Student Evaluations at the Intersection of Gender and STEM. *Summer Robinson, University of Houston; Paul Anthony Turcotte, University of Houston; Virginia W. Snodgrass Rangel, University of Houston; Nia*

Soeharto, University of Houston; Mark Clarke, University of Houston; Robert McPherson, University of Houston

Chair: *Seonmi Jin, Indiana University*

Discussant: *Ebelia Hernandez, Rutgers University*

34.034. Critical (re)construction in Teacher Education:

Inclusive Race, Disability, and Language. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 8;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Reimagining Educator Competence: Framework for Multilingual Learners with and without Literacy-Based Learning Dis/Abilities. *Tipsuda Chaomuangkhong, Arizona State University; Monaliza M Chian, University of Northern Iowa; David I. Hernandez-Saca, University of Northern Iowa*

"She Corrected Me, But She Didn't Make Me Feel Small": Rewriting the Emotional Terms of Inclusion in K-12 Classrooms. *Hyun Uk Kim, Springfield College*

"She has no business in dual language:" A Critique of Current Inequitable (dis)Placement Trends in a Two-Way Dual Language Program. *Dora Diaz, University of Texas at Austin*

"Tuning In" to Children's Brilliance: Families' Contributions to UDL's 3.0 Guidelines to Prepare Teachers/Educators. *Cristina C. Santamaria Graff, Indiana University - Indianapolis; Yone Rodriguez, Claremont Graduate University*

Chairs: *Aubry D. Threlkeld, Harvard University; Tipsuda Chaomuangkhong, Arizona State University*

Discussant: *Aubry D. Threlkeld, Harvard University*

34.035. Dis/ability and Neurodiversity: Untangling Our Roots to Embody Equity and Justice. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Symposium JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 6; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Dis/ability and Neurodiversity: Untangling Our Roots to Embody Equity and Justice. *Molly Elizabeth Siuty, Temple University*

Neurodiversity and Dis/ability: Untangling Our Roots to Embody Equity and Justice. *Niki Elliott, University of San Diego*

Untangling Our Roots to Embody Equity and Justice. *Victoria Graf, Loyola Marymount University*

Chair: *Victoria Graf, Loyola Marymount University*

Discussant: *Victoria Graf, Loyola Marymount University*

34.036. Innovations in Pre-Service Teacher Education: Supporting Equity, Language, and Global Citizenship.

Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 9;

9:45-11:15am

Participants:

A Measure of Preservice Teacher Self-Efficacy for Working with Emergent Bilingual Students. *Jasmine Barahona, University of Oregon; Monica Romero, University of Texas at Austin*

Analyzing University Syllabi in Korea Through UNESCO's Lens: Global Citizenship Education for Pre-Service Secondary Teachers. *Yura Oh, Stanford University*

A(n) (Re)awakening: Preservice Teachers Connecting Their Culture to Science Teaching Along the U.S.-Mexico Border. *Angela Chapman, University of Texas - Rio Grande Valley; William Medina Jerez, University of Texas - El Paso; Janine M. Schall, University of Texas - Rio Grande Valley; Uma Maheshwari Ganesan, University of Texas - Rio Grande Valley; Mourat Tchoshanov, The University of Texas - El Paso; Ruby Lynch-Arroyo, University of New Mexico; Miriam M. Ortiz, University of Texas - Rio Grande Valley*

Case Study of Dual Language Teacher Certification: New Evidence-based Solutions to the National Teacher Shortage. *Ganze Karaer, Washington State University; Anne Marie Guerrettaz, Washington State University; Genoveva Vega, Washington State University; Yun-Ju Hsiao, Washington State University - Tri-Cities; Yuliya Ardasheva, Washington State University - Tri-Cities; Shenghai Dai, Washington State University; Danica Garcia, Washington State University - Tri-Cities; Lindsay K. Lightner, Washington State University; Onur Ramazan, University of Hong Kong; Adam Ulysess Coldiron, Washington State University*

From Awareness to Agency: Navigating Equity in Chinese TESOL Practicums. *Edith M. Y. Yan, Beijing Normal-Hong Kong Baptist University*

Discussant: *Rosie Ojeda, California Polytechnic State University - San Luis Obispo*

34.037. Reimagining Mentor Support: Learning, Positionality, and Equity in Teacher Residency Programs. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Symposium JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 1; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Reimagining Teaching Retention by Supporting Mentor Teachers. *Melissa Sachi Arias, University of California - Los Angeles; Emma D. Hipolito, University of California - Los Angeles; Imelda Nava-Landeros, University of California - Los Angeles*

From Vision to Practice: Aligning Cooperating Teachers with Program Mission/Vision for Cohesive Teacher Preparation. *Frances Valdovinos, University of California - Riverside*

Unforgetting Mentor Histories: Exploring Professional Learning Journeys That Shape Teacher Mentorship. *Francesca Henderson, University of Maryland*

Chair: *Emma D. Hipolito, University of California - Los Angeles*

Discussant: *Cathy Yun, Learning Policy Institute*

34.038. Sustaining Commitments: Identity and Social Justice in Teacher Education. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 7;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

The Influence of Identity on Preservice Teachers' Development and Engagement in Asset-Based, Critical Race Pedagogies. *Jessica N. Hiltabidel, George Mason University*

The Long-Term Impact of Critical Narrative Ethnography on Teacher Commitment to Social Justice. *Megan Corinne Samaniego, Claremont Graduate University*

Unraveling Justice Teacher Education Programs from within: Voices of Institutions, Teacher Educators and Preservice Teachers. *Catalina Cuenca, Universidad Alberto Hurtado*

Asian American Teachers, Anti-Asian Racism, and COVID-19. *Grace MyHyun Kim, University of Texas at Austin; North Cooc, University of Texas at Austin*

Building Bridges: A Literature Review of Authentic Relationships in White-Dominated Educational Spaces. *Maggan Quist, University of Nebraska - Lincoln*

Chair: *Jessica N. Hiltabidel, George Mason University*

Discussant: *Terry Stockton, Grand Valley State University*

34.039. Teaching In the Wake: Racial Justice Praxis Across Teacher Education, Classrooms, and Schools. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 2;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

"Wounded Healers": Movement, Memory, and Cultural Meaning-Making Through Performance Pedagogy in Teacher Education. *Beth Beschorner, Minnesota State University - Mankato; Timothy Berry, Minnesota State University - Mankato*

For what is a tortilla a pedagogical prop?: Nuancing food for food justice and culturally sustaining pedagogy in classrooms. *Terrance Burgess, Michigan State University; Terry K. Flenbaugh, Michigan State University; Kyle L. Chong, Michigan State University*

Racial Literacy Teacher/Leader Modules: Alignment and Actualizing a Justice Imperative. *Laurie D. Inman, California State University - Dominguez Hills; Edward R. Curammeng, California State University - Dominguez Hills*

Strategic Alliances and Fugitivity: Advancing Racial Justice in Educator Preparation Amidst Legislative Constraints. *Markita C Warren, Cleveland State University; Katherine Clonan-Roy, Cleveland State University; Tristta M. Kuykendall, Cleveland State University; Marketa Fuller-President, Cleveland State University*

Chair: *Klaudia Burton, Michigan State University*

Discussant: *Daniel Morales-Doyle, University of Illinois at Chicago*

34.040. Governing Democracy: School Boards, Elections, and Local Policy Responses. Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 10; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Do Partisan Elections Change School Board Policies or Just Who Sits on Them? *Shelby Buono Shumard, College of Charleston*

Proximity Politics: Explaining Political Behavior in School Board Elections. *Jonathan E. Collins, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Beyond Compliance: Reclaiming Governance through School-Community Partnerships and Culturally Sustaining Values. *La Toya Caton, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Critical Discourse Analysis: San Diego County School District Responses to Immigration Policies. *Ambrosia Daphne Solis, University of California - Riverside*

Chair: *Catherine Kramarczuk Voulgarides, Hunter College - CUNY*

Discussant: *James C. Bridgforth, University of Delaware*

SIG Sessions

34.041. Critical Reflections from Equity-Minded Asian/American Education Leaders on What's Next in the Post-2024 World. SIG-Asian Americans and Pacific Islanders in Education and Research; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 309;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

"You are Young, That's Why We Hired You:" How Hiring Managers Can Increase the Sense of Belonging in Young Administrators. *Nicholas Daniel Hartlep, Berea College*

To be Radical, Asian/American, and Dean?: Negotiating the Racial Capitalism of Higher Education Leadership and (Trying) to Stay True to Self. *Wayne Au, University of Washington - Bothell*

Navigating Expectations of Silence: Being Bold, Speaking Out, and Challenging Assumptions. *Yune Kim Tran, Providence College*

Disrupting Racial Triangulation in a Fragile Post-2020 Context: Counter-Perspectives from an Asian/American Woman Leader. *Rachel Endo, University of Washington - Tacoma*

Troubling and Reframing Progress & Progressive: Queer+Asian Lenses for Anti-Oppressive Leading. *Kevin Kumashiro, Independent Consultant*

Creating Positive, Affirming Spaces for the Development of Counter-Narratives for Teacher Education Students from Immigrant and Refugee Backgrounds. *Kevin C. Roxas, Western Washington University*

Chair: *Lin Wu, Western Oregon University*

Discussant: *Roland Sintos Coloma, Wayne State University*

34.042. Translanguaging, Multimodality and Affect in School and Community Learning Ecologies. SIG-Bilingual Education Research; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 501B;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Teachers' Translanguaging Beliefs and Practice in Science.
Margarita Anahi Rodriguez, University of California - Santa Barbara

Multimodal, embodied practices in culturally sustaining, translanguaging group read-alouds for young emergent bilinguals. *Mallory Paige Woods, University of California - Santa Barbara*

Promotora-Child Metalinguistic Conversations in a Preschool Mixteco Heritage learning Program. *Amelia (Amy) Kyratzis, University of California - Santa Barbara*

Transnational Dreams, Translanguaging Tongues, and the Making of Qazaqness in Los Angeles' Little Kazakhstan. *Munira Kairat, University of California - Santa Barbara*

Multivoiced Participation: Footing and Heteroglossia in Bilingual Children's Heritage Language Learning. *ZeJia Xu, Uppsala University; Ann-Carita Evaldsson, Uppsala University, Sweden*

"Teacher, are those words how you spell in Arabic?": Socializing Linguistic and Cultural Awareness through Metalinguistic Conversations in Preschool. *Hanna Asmaeil, University of California - Santa Barbara*

Chair: *Amelia (Amy) Kyratzis, University of California - Santa Barbara*

34.043. Student Learning, AI, and Digital Tools. SIG-Computer and Internet Application in Education; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, San Bernardino; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Beyond the Avatar: Developing Digital Resilience for Collaborative Learning in Virtual Worlds. *Miri Shonfeld, Kibbutzin College; Merav Hayak, Columbia University; Achva Academic College; Ben-Gurion University of the Negev; Orit Avidov-Ungar, Achva Academic College*

Beyond the Badge: Fostering Motivational Internalization in Programming Education Through a Need-Supportive Educational Game. *Fan Zou, Sichuan Normal University; Xiaoqian Wang, Sichuan Normal University*

Does Internet Use Influence Science Performance Directly and Indirectly Through ICT Self-Efficacy and Science Self-Efficacy? *Sunha Kim, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Hyeonji Jeong, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Wei Wang, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Dris Prophete, University at Buffalo - SUNY; John E. Slaughter, Learning, Education, and Development Services*

Middle School Multilingual Learners and AI Chatbots:

Navigating Comparison/Contrast Writing. *Ying Zhang, Robert Morris University; Xiaojun Chen, St. John's University*

Profiles of Postgraduate Students' Use of Artificial Intelligence in Writing: Antecedents and Outcomes. *Fangzhou Jin, The University of Hong Kong; Chun Lai, The University of Hong Kong; Chin-Hsi Lin, University of Hong Kong*

Chair: *Kyungbin Kwon, Indiana University*

Discussant: *Ugur Kale, Indiana University*

34.044. Healing and Trauma Across Learning Contexts: BIPOC Youth Perspectives and Practices. SIG-Critical Educators for Social Justice; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304B;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

"Life is really worth living": Cultivating Latinx Young People's Experiences of Radical Healing. *Saraí Blanco Martinez, University of Michigan*

(Re)Writing Literacy Relationships: Tracing Writing Memories, Literacy Trauma, and Healing for Girls of Color. *Catherine Ventura, University of Michigan*

Escaping Surveillance and Belonging Outside: Investigating Place-Based Education, Fugitivity, and Racial Healing for Black Youth. *Marquise Griffin, University of Michigan*

Chair: *Sharim Hannegan-Martinez, University of Michigan*

Discussant: *Ayleen Correa, University of Michigan*

34.045. Beyond Histories of Compliance in Early Childhood Education: Centering Disability and Cultivating Freedom. SIG-Critical Perspectives on Early Childhood Education; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 511C;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Dialogue 1: Cultivating Relationships with and Between Young Children. *April Coloma Boyce, University of Washington; Malcom L King, University of Washington; Bárbara Silveira Baptista de Oliveira, Pennsylvania State University; Ana Luisa Borba Gediel, Federal University of Viçosa*

Dialogue 2: Enacting Pedagogical Resistance in Early Learning Contexts. *Devanshi Unadkat, San Diego State University; Caroline Cuenca, University of San Francisco; Kathryn Meyer, Binghamton University - SUNY; Rosie Tuffour-Mercadat, Independent Scholar; Elizabeth Barcay, Boston University; Brianna Doherty, Independent Scholar; A.R. Shearer, Independent Scholar; Jasmin Stoffer, Independent Scholar; Ame Christiansen, University of Melbourne*

Dialogue 3: Prioritizing Families' Perspectives and Stories. *Nickie Coomer, Colorado College; Teukie Martin, Syracuse University; William A. Proffitt, Montclair State University; Colleen M. Campbell, University of California - Santa Cruz; Rae L. Tewa, Arizona State University; Elizabeth A. Ruiz, Arizona State University; Nicole S. Begay, Arizona State*

University

Dialogue 4: Engaging in Critical Praxis in Educator Preparation. *Hailey Love, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Maggie Beneke, University of Washington; Lilly Padia, Erikson Institute; Crystasany R. Turner, University of Wisconsin - Milwaukee; Maria Rosa Brea-Spahn, New York University; Xigrad Soto-Boykin, Arizona State University*

Chairs: *Maggie Beneke, University of Washington; Hailey Love, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Discussant: *Tran Templeton, Teachers College, Columbia University*

34.046. Foucault in Education: Generative Dialogues on Power, Knowledge, and Resistance Across Theory, Practice, and Method. SIG-Critical Posthuman and Postfoundational Studies in Education; Symposium JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 3; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Activism and Resistance in Global Education. *Emily Yerkes, University of Colorado - Boulder; Laurie Gutmann Kahn, Moravian University; Lei Zheng, Peking University*
Historicizing Educational Knowledge and Practice. *Sun Young Lee, Wichita State University; Thomas S. Popkewitz, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Elsa Roland, Université de Namur*

Emerging Trends and Global Perspectives. *Mariam Sedighi, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Marino Miranda Noriega, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Robert Allen Smith, The University of North Carolina School of the Arts*
Institutional Dynamics. *Ezequiel Gomez Caride, Universidad de San Andrés; Jinting Wu, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Michael Edmond Skyer, University of Tennessee*

Subject Formation and Education. *Matthew Cook; Robert J. Helfenbein, Mercer University*

Theoretical Foundations and Methodological Implications. *Junzi Huang, Peking University*

Chairs: *Rouhollah Aghasaleh, California State Polytechnic University - Humboldt; Tristan G. Gleason, California State Polytechnic University - Humboldt*

Discussants: *James P. Burns, University of New Mexico; Christopher M. Kirchgasser, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

34.047. Feminist Critique, Praxis and Relationality in Education. SIG-Decolonial, Postcolonial, and Anti-Colonial Studies in Education; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 303B; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Feminista Pláticas Across Borders: Theorizing Journeys of Belonging and Resistance in Academia. *Leila Mouhib, Université Libre de Bruxelles; Zehra Colak, Utrecht University; Raquel Sáenz Ortiz, Southwestern University*

Palestinian Feminist Praxis as Decolonial Refusal: Reclaiming Education, Memory, and Liberation. *Amanda Najib, New York University*

Speaking While Silenced: Reflections of Black Sistahs Within Colonial Spaces of Education: A Black Feminist Critique of Inclusion in Global Disability Discourse. *Jocelyn Belden, Georgia State University; Krystal Anderson, University of California - Berkeley; Danica T. Moise, University of Central Florida; Tranika Jefferson, Black Association of Behavior Analysis; Alia Bonnerel, Charter Behavior Management; Sharde Theodore, OSEP*

Unforgetting Together: Feminist Relationality as Method, Praxis, and Future. *Dianne T. Wellington, SUNY - College at Cortland; Amy Walker, Kent State University; Shannon Athey, West Chester University of Pennsylvania; Sharon Daley, Indiana University; Hyunjeong Lee, Indiana University; Shaunta D. Scroggins, Purdue University; Breanya Hogue, Purdue University; Jessica McClain, Indiana University*

Critical Consciousness in Motion: Pakistani Women Scholars Unforgetting Histories and Imagining Futures for Decolonizing Education. *Tahreem Fatima, Miami University (OH); Moaaz Hamid, Indiana University*

Chair: *Alexandra Allweiss, Michigan State University*

Discussant: *Alessandra Romano, University of Siena*

34.048. Discussing Controversial Issues in Class: Classroom Climate, Critical Consciousness, and Civic Competence. SIG-Democratic Citizenship in Education; Symposium JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Georgia II; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Associations Between Open Classroom Climate and Political Knowledge: A Meta-Analysis. *Elisabeth Graf, TU Dortmund University; Pascal Alscher, TU Dortmund University; Daniel Deimel, University of Duisburg-Essen*
The Reciprocal Link Between Civic Literacy and Open Classroom Climate: A Longitudinal Perspective. *Pascal Alscher, TU Dortmund University; Daniel Deimel, University of Duisburg-Essen; Elisabeth Graf, TU Dortmund University*

Politically Curious: Ideological Identity and How High School Students Experience Controversy. *Gregory E. McAvoy, University of North Carolina - Greensboro; Paula McAvoy, North Carolina State University; Davis Harper, North Carolina State University*

Social Justice Education and Adolescents' Critical Consciousness Development. *Laura Wray-Lake, University of Rochester; Elan Hope, North Carolina State University; Christopher Wegemer, University of California - Los Angeles; Allison Weber, Policy Research Associates; Emily Greytak, ACLU*

Chairs: *Elisabeth Graf, TU Dortmund University; Pascal Alscher, TU Dortmund University; Daniel Deimel, University of*

Duisburg-Essen

Discussant: *David E. Campbell, University of Notre Dame*

34.049. Digging in the Crates: Sampling as Archival Practice and Pedagogical Method. SIG-Hip Hop Theories, Praxis & Pedagogies; Demonstration/Performance

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Atrium III; 9:45-11:15am

Participant:

“Buying Old Records is a Habit”: Digging in the Crates as Archival Practice. *Jason D. Rawls, The Ohio State University*

Chair: *Stevie D. Johnson, The Ohio State University*

34.050. Truth and Healing in California: Land, Education, and the Remembering, Restorying, Reclaiming Project. SIG-Indigenous Peoples of the Americas; Symposium

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Georgia I; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Remembering in the Wake of Erasure: Reclaiming Research as an Act of Unforgetting. *Kelly Leah Stewart, University of California, Los Angeles*

Restorying the Land: Reframing Institutional Responsibility on Native Homelands. *Theresa J. Stewart-Ambo, University of California - Los Angeles*

Reclaiming the Archive: Reading Bureaucratic Silence through Indigenous Memory. *Heather Ponchetti Daly, University of California - San Diego*

Weaving Futures Together: Building Research through Relational Accountability. *Patricia D. Quijada Cerecer, University of California - Davis*

Healing on Our Own Terms: Returning Memory through Research and Ceremony. *Magdalena Sunshine Serrano, Community Health Centers of the Central Coast*

Chair: *Kehaulani Natsuko Vaughn, University of Utah*

Discussant: *Charles Sepulveda, The University of Utah*

34.051. Differing Perspectives on School Improvement. SIG-Innovative School Transformation and Reform; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Atrium I; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

A Comparative Actor-Network Study of Future Learning Centers in Chinese and American Universities. *Tao Xu, Tongji University; Yulin Wu, Tongji University*

Implementing Student-Driven Projects in a Korean Learner-Centered Middle School. *Yeol Huh, Kennesaw State University; Dabae Lee, Kennesaw State University; Eunbae Lee, Kyung Hee University*

Turnaround, Crisis, and Recovery: Neoliberal Subjectivities and Contracting Processes for District-Charter Turnaround Partnerships in Texas. *Alejandro Madrigal, University of*

Texas at Austin; Daniel Dawer, University of Texas at Austin

Chair: *Vanessa Hammler Kenon, University of Texas - San Antonio*

Discussant: *Patience Amadu, University of Colorado - Colorado Springs*

34.052. The Role of Educational Policy in a Democratic Republic, as Framed by the Constitution and the Courts.

SIG-Law and Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Plaza II; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Critical Legal Literacy: Reclaiming the Law as a Tool for Democratic Futures in Education. *Christopher D. Thomas, University of Florida; Jamie Kudlats, University of North Carolina - Charlotte*

Beyond Left and Right: Reframing “Intellectual Diversity” through Critical Knowledge Praxis in Higher Education Policy. *Michael Martinez, New York University*

Educational Implications of the Supreme Court’s Abandonment of the Historical “Balanced Neutrality” Toward Religion.

Jonathon E. Sawyer, University of Colorado - Boulder; Kevin G. Welner, University of Colorado - Boulder

Mahmoud v. Taylor: New interpretations of the Free Exercise Clause and Curriculum concerns. *Nicholas E. Mitchell, University of Kansas*

School Leaders And Educational Governance - At The Interplay Between Law, Curriculum And Education. *Ragnhild Meland, University of Oslo; Jeffrey Brooks Hall, University of Oslo*

Chair: *Kelly Ann Peña, Rutgers University*

34.053. Constructing and (Re)imagining Educational Leadership Through the Use of Case Studies. SIG-Learning and Teaching in Educational Leadership; Symposium

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Palos Verdes; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Can the Cycle Be Broken? Latina Superintendents, the Glass Cliff, and Systemic Inequities. *Angelina Gutierrez, Texas Christian University; Nancy Cruz Rodriguez, Texas Christian University*

Promotion or Retention? A Texas Senior’s Dilemma. *Sonia Brown, Texas Christian University; Zarvonnia Gibbs, Texas Christian University; Ron Mendoza, Texas Christian University*

Under Pressure: One Principal’s Navigation through Racial Tension. *Maria O’Connor, Texas Christian University; Lori Wilson, Texas Christian University*

Superintendent-School Board Conflict: Navigating Politics in District Leadership. *Kailey Penn, Texas Christian University; Bel Williams, Texas Christian University*

Chair: *Jo Beth Jimerson, Texas Christian University*

Discussant: *Miriam Deborah Ezzani, Texas Christian University*

34.054. Digital Ecologies of Hope: A Natural History of Emerging Media Futures. SIG-Media, Culture, and Learning; Structured Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 515B;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

1. SPECIMEN #2025-A: Aspirational AI Self-Imaging (Poster 1). *Ioana Literat, Teachers College, Columbia University*
2. SPECIMEN #2025-B: Video Testimony and/as Collective Witnessing (Poster 2). *Sonia Kim, Teachers College, Columbia University*
3. SPECIMEN #2025-C: Freedom Dreamers: Collective Care in the Cloud (Poster 3). *Andrea Kim, Teachers College, Columbia University*
4. SPECIMEN #2025-D: POVs as Self-Dialogues Across Time: Digital Rituals of Recovery from Diet Culture (Poster 4). *Madison Smith, Teachers College, Columbia University*
5. SPECIMEN #2025-E: Screens of Possibility: Resilience and Connectivity among Sudanese Youth (Poster 5). *Abubakr Abdelbagi, Teachers College, Columbia University*
6. SPECIMEN #2025-F: Digital Sanctuaries: Afro-Brazilian Identity in Elite Academic Spaces (Poster 6). *Inara Bezerra Ferreira de Sousa, Teachers College, Columbia University*
7. SPECIMEN #2025-G: Friction as Pedagogy: AI Debates in Educator Networks (Poster 7). *Rhea Jaffer, Teachers College, Columbia University*
8. SPECIMEN #2025-H: #MyVoiceOnT: Transgender Voice Documentation on TikTok (Poster 8). *Sara Meier Clark, Teachers College, Columbia University*
9. SPECIMEN #2025-I: Digital Playlists as Reflection and Refuge in an Israeli-Palestinian Research Collective (Poster 9). *Shoshana Gottesman, Teachers College, Columbia University*
10. SPECIMEN #2025-J: Recess Therapy and the Radical Wisdom of Children (Poster 10). *Julio Intriago Izquierdo, Teachers College, Columbia University*
11. SPECIMEN #2025-K: Algospeak: Linguistic Evolution in Algorithmic Ecosystems (Poster 11). *Shell Avenant, Teachers College, Columbia University*
12. SPECIMEN #2025-L: The Laboratory of Hope: Digital Habitats of Persistence and Problem-Solving (Poster 12). *Carolina Soterio, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Chair: *Lalitha Vasudevan, Teachers College, Columbia University*

34.055. Mapping the Long Haul: Cartographies of Mentoring Journeys. SIG-Mentorship and Mentoring Practices; Symposium

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, La Brea; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Journeys of Becoming: Mapping Our Lives Through Mentoring Relationships. *Kimberly N. Williams Brown, Vassar College; Faith D. Northern, New York University; Cayla Kallman,*

Vassar College; Malachi Derian Maguregui, The School District of Philadelphia

Re-Authoring Mentoring Experiences: Counter-Mapping Untold Stories. *Ines Gill Grill, Colleague of Science, Technology and Applied Arts of Trinidad and Tobago, Trinidad and Tobago; Tamara Phillip, The College of Science, Technology and Applied Arts of Trinidad and Tobago (COSTAATT); Laurette Maria Stacy Bristol, University of the West Indies - Cave Hill*

Mapping Juneberries: Imagining a Future for Mentoring Graduate and Undergraduate Students in STEM Disciplines. *Jillian Cadwell, Washington State University - Tri-Cities; Ke Wu, Montana State University; Makini Beck, Rochester Institute of Technology; Melinda Howard, Gonzaga University; Elizabeth Wargo, University of Idaho; Veronica S. Smith, data2insight LLC*

Sisterhood Spirit Mapping Our Health, Wealth, and Inspiration. *Antonette M. Aragon, Colorado State University; Christine W Nganga, The George Washington University; Makini Beck, Rochester Institute of Technology*

Woke-r Jokers in it for the Long Haul: Mapping mentoring networks (CYF model for Jokers PlayL) through Professional Development. *Vonzell Agosto, University of South Florida; Deirdre Cobb-Roberts, University of South Florida; Talia Esnard, University of the West Indies - St. Augustine*

Imagining Education Otherwise: Mapping Mentorship, Networks, and the Power of Remembering. *Dina Pacis, National University San Diego; Anne Ritter, National University; Nilisa J. Thorsos, National University*

Chair: *Maniphone S. Dickerson, San Jose City College*
Discussant: *Paula Morris, The Academy Charter School*

34.056. Course Grade Policies: What are the Consequences for Motivation, Achievement, and Equity? SIG-Motivation in Education; Symposium

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Santa Barbara C; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Undergraduate instructors' beliefs about students' abilities relate to their course policies and student outcomes. *Lisa B Limeri, Texas Tech University; Rosario Andrea Marroquin-Flores, James Madison University; Mozhdeh Forghaniarani, James Madison University; Katherine M. Muenks, University of Texas at Austin; Madison Pakenham, Texas Tech University; Chance Pavlock, Texas Tech University; Ivana Raj, Texas Tech University; Sarah Ronda, Texas Tech University; Amy Rudick, Texas Tech University; Amber Sena, Texas Tech University*

How Grading Policies Relate to Students' Perceptions of Teachers' Beliefs. *Shengjie Lin, University of New Mexico; Yu-Yu Hsiao, University of New Mexico; Jennifer Jordan, University of New Mexico; Yiqiu Yan, University of Texas at Austin*

Panic and Hope, Pressure and Redemption: College Students' Motivational Responses to Course Grade Policies. *Julie Sievers, University of Texas at Austin; Katherine M. Muenks, University of Texas at Austin*

An Autoethnographic Exploration of Ungrading and Faculty Motivation Off the Tenure Track. *Allison Zengilowski, Lehigh University*

The Motivational Consequences of Grading Policies: A Multilevel, Equity-Focused Interpretation. *Alison C. Koenka, University of Oklahoma; Korinthia D. Nicolai, Indiana University; Destini N. Braxton, University of Virginia; Margaret K. Powers, Washington University in St. Louis; Danielle N. Berry, University of Oklahoma; Sandra Graham, University of California - Los Angeles; Kanvarbir Gill, University of Oklahoma*

Chairs: *Katherine M. Muenks, University of Texas at Austin; Julie Sievers, University of Texas at Austin*

Discussant: *Carlton J. Fong, Texas State University*

34.057. Unforgetting Difficult Knowledge and Constructing Possibilities through Narrative Research. SIG-Narrative Research; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum J; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Navigating the Null Lived Curriculum of Grief: Difficult Knowledge, Narrative Research and Speaking the Unspeakable. *Sara Simpson, University of Texas Rio Grande Valley*

Missing Chromosomes, Found Identity: Difficult Knowledge, Narrative Research and the Intersectional Lived Curriculum of Turner Syndrome. *Ivana Maldonado, University of Texas - Rio Grande Valley*

When School Hurts: An Autoethnographic Narrative Navigating the Dark Knowledge of Abusive Neglect within the Special Education System as a Mother, Educator, and Advocate. *Elizabeth Sherley, University of Texas Rio Grande Valley*

Chair: *Laura M. Jewett, University of Texas - Rio Grande Valley*

Discussant: *Laura M. Jewett, University of Texas - Rio Grande Valley*

34.058. Informed Consent in Online Education Research, Evaluation, and Learning Analytics. SIG-Online Teaching and Learning; Symposium
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, La Cienega; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Informed Consent in Research with Online Students: Frameworks and Policies. *Mary Ellen Dello Stritto, Oregon State University*

Synthesizing Informed Consent Practices in Learning Analytics. *Gabriel N Montes de Oca, Boise State University*
Power, Consent, and Transparency: Stakeholder Perspectives of

Learning Analytics. *Rebecca E. Heiser, Athabasca University; Margaretta Underhill, Oregon State University*
The Use of AI in Research: Creating a Culture of Consent. *Margaretta Underhill, Oregon State University*

Chair: *Amy Vecchione, Boise State University*

Discussant: *Amy Vecchione, Boise State University*

34.059. The Politics of Education in Politicized Times: Democracy, Knowledge, and Policy. SIG-Politics of Education; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Plaza III; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Responding to Manufactured Ignorance: Knowledge, Emotions, and Democratic Trust. *Penelope Lusk, University of Pennsylvania; Sigal R. Ben-Porath, University of Pennsylvania*

Civic Burden: Conceptualizing the Epistemic Harms of Traditional Civic Education Curriculum. *Abigail Dym, Providence College*

The Educated State: Competing and Complementary Policy Alliances in Public Education. *Nora Reikosky, University of Houston*

Chair: *Pamela L. Grossman, University of Pennsylvania*

Discussant: *Rehana Odendaal, University of Pennsylvania*

34.060. "We are not a monolith": Expanding Blackness Through the Intersections. SIG-Queer Studies; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Beaudry A; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Beyond Survival and Toward Thriving: An Exploration of Black Queer and Trans College Student Well-being. *Dion Tremain Harry, Oklahoma State University*

Black Queer Youths' Invitations to Researcher Self-Revelation. *Mara D. Johnson, University of Michigan*

Looking for Black Lesbian Life in the Archives: Reclaiming My Story Through Critical Fabulation. *Kristina Johnson-Yates, Indiana University - Indianapolis*

Resist! Reimagine! Reclaim!: Centering Black Queer and Trans Activism, Pedagogies and Futures. *William Shelton, Graduate Center - CUNY*

"You're Too Smart to Be Straight, You Must Be Gay": Black Masculinity, Academic Identity Regulation, and Gender Performance in Alabama's Black Belt. *Shelton K. Johnson, SUNY New Paltz*

34.061. Archive to Unforget: Educational Geographies of Remembering, Reclaiming & the Recovery of Our Collective Memory. SIG-Research Focus on Black Education; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304C; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

The Art of Archival Activism: Youth Speculative Archiving through Spatial Histories in Chicago's West Side. *Kaleb Germinaro, University of Illinois at Chicago*

Fugitive Poetry Pedagogies for the People. *Christopher R. Rogers, Haverford College*

The Black Atlas: Reimagining Space and Resistance Through Green Book Methodologies. *Jessica Lee Stovall, University of Wisconsin - Madison; hailey elizabeth schock, University of Wisconsin - LaCrosse; Jada Young, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Joy is a place we make: Exploring sisterhood and political imagination in Black college women's placemaking. *Gordon Palmer, University of Illinois at Chicago*

Charting an Otherwise: Black Girls Designing for Collective Access. *Jazmen Moore, Stony Brook University - SUNY*

You Won't Forget Us: Black Girls Using Altar Practices to Map Their Lives. *Aja Reynolds, Wayne State University*

Chairs: *Aja Reynolds, Wayne State University; Kaleb Germinaro, University of Illinois at Chicago*

Discussant: *Dana Gabrielle Nickson, University of Washington*

34.062. Data, Play, and Power: Sports as Culturally

Sustaining Learning Sites. SIG-Research Focus on Education and Sport; Working Group Roundtable Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 501A; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

The 'Real Ticket': Reimagining Social Mobility for Black Athletes in the Era of NIL. *Lien Amin, University of Colorado - Boulder*

Big Fish or Little Pond? National Evidence on the Relationship between Transferring and Athletic Performance within Division I Men's College Basketball. *Kendall Cole, Stanford University; Francis A. Pearman, Stanford University*

The GRIND: Generative Research and Inclusive Networks in Data as a Site for Equitable STEM Identity. *Kareem Edouard, Drexel University; Marcelo A.B. Worsley, Northwestern University*

Applying the Computer Science Capital Framework: Understanding Computing Engagement Among Student-Athletes. *Michael Smith, Northwestern University; Ashley Serine Quiterio, Northwestern University; Jacob Puthipiroj, Northwestern University*

Chair: *Kareem Edouard, Drexel University*

34.063. Research on the Superintendency SIG 97 Paper Session. SIG-Research on the Superintendency; Paper Session

Westin Bonaventure, Level 2, Mt. Washington; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

More Than Mentorship: Black Women Superintendents and the Bonds of Sisterhood. *Anna Jackman, NYC Public Schools;*

Sonya Douglass, Teachers College, Columbia University
The Shifting Role Conceptualizations of the Superintendency. *Christopher H. Tienken, Seton Hall University; Jennifer Timmer, Seton Hall University*

The Unification Story: Transforming New Orleans Schools. *Henderson Lewis, Louisiana State University*

Discussant: *Jentre J. Olsen, Oklahoma State University*

34.064. AI Innovations in Language and Literacy Education for K-12 Multilingual Learners. SIG-Second Language Research; Symposium

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum A; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Generative Artificial Intelligence in the Assessment of Young Multilingual Learners' Productive Language Skills. *Becky H. Huang, The Ohio State University*

Leveraging AI to Uncover Linguistic Profiles and Inform Instruction for K-12 Multilingual Learners. *Eunice Eunhee Jang, University of Toronto - OISE; Angelie Ignacio, University of Toronto - OISE; Hajung Kim, University of Toronto - OISE; Han Lai, University of Toronto; Heidi Kenkel, University of Toronto - OISE*

Exploring K-12 Multilingual Learners' Use and Perceptions of an AI Writing Feedback Tool. *Mikyung Kim Wolf, ETS; Michael Suhan, ETS*

Chair: *Mikyung Kim Wolf, ETS*

Discussant: *Zhongfeng Tian, Rutgers University - Newark*

34.065. Supporting Across the Stages of Teacher Development: Self-Studies of Mentorship for Pre-service, Graduate, and Doctoral Students. SIG-Self-Study of Teacher Education Practices; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Plaza I; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Examining Faculty Feedback to Graduate Students: A Collaborative Self-Study. *Mary Antony Bair, Grand Valley State University; David E. Bair, Grand Valley State University*

Exploring the Newness of Welcoming International Preservice Teachers in Teacher Education: A Collaborative Self-Study. *Robert J. Campbell, St. Mary's University College; Rachel Davies, King's College London; Daniel Cottle, University of Birmingham; Caroline Neuberger, Leeds Trinity University; Eleanor Wylie, Institute of Physics*

Exploring the Supervisory Practices and Written Feedback for a Self-Study Dissertation. *Jason K. Ritter, Duquesne University*

Reimagining Culturally Responsive Pedagogy for International Students in Higher Education. *Eugenia Vomvoridi-Ivanovic, University of South Florida; Sophia Han, University of South Florida; Jennifer Jacobs, University of South Florida; Zorka Karanxha, University of South Florida*

Using Memory-Work to Articulate the Purpose for Engaging in Photovoice with Mathematics Specialist Candidates.

Katherine Edwards, George Mason University; Courtney Baker, George Mason University

Chair: *Katie F. Whitley, Montclair State University*

Discussant: *Amanda Moody Maestranzi, Lehman College - CUNY*

34.066. Centering Youth Voices and Experiences in Social and Emotional Learning Research. SIG-Social and Emotional Learning; Symposium

Westin Bonaventure, Level 3, Santa Monica B; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Love Is Infinite: Bringing Youth Voices in Envisioning Social Emotional Learning for Indigenous Youth. *Jingjing Sun, University of Montana; Anisa Goforth, University of Montana; Deborah Ith, University of Montana - Missoula; Niki Graham, University of Montana*

How Do At-Risk Youth Evaluate the Social, Emotional, and Behavioral Impacts of A Mindful Choice Curriculum? *Manisha Naresh Nagpal, Duquesne University*

Centering Youth Voices in Math and SEL: A Quasi-Experimental Pilot Study. *Luz Robinson, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Hannah Garner; Graceson L. Clements, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Grace Little; Victoria Plyler; Dorothy L. Espelage, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Todd S. Cherner, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Marisa Marraccini, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*

Chair: *Jingjing Sun, University of Montana*

Discussant: *Dorothy L. Espelage, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*

34.067. Fifty Years of Push and Pull: Challenging Assumptions about Inclusion Within Traditional Special Education Discourse. SIG-Special and Inclusive Education Research; Symposium

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum I; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

The Rhetorics of (Re)Branding: A Historical and Discourse Analysis of the Inclusion/ Special Education Debate. *Julia M. White, Syracuse University; Christine Elaine Ashby, Syracuse University; Rebekah Wallis, Syracuse University; Ethan W Jackson, Syracuse University; Cam Michael Powell, Syracuse University*

Shifting the Policy Debate to Challenging the Ableism in Special Education Policy and Practice. *Jennifer A. Kurth, University of Kansas; Karrie A. Shogren, University of Kansas*

Where is the Empirical Evidence? *Megan E. Carpenter, Clemson University; Kristin K. Burnette, East Carolina University; Charlene Loope, East Carolina University; Susan Gollighugh, Montgomery Independent School District;*

Rebecca Smith Heinze, University of Arizona

Education Policy: Does Special Education “Do No Harm”?

Deborah Taub, OTL Education Solutions; Diane L Ryndak, University of North Carolina - Greensboro; Julia M. White, Syracuse University; Christine Elaine Ashby, Syracuse University; Rebekah Wallis, Syracuse University; Cam Michael Powell, Syracuse University; Ethan W Jackson, Syracuse University

Going Back to the Future? (Re)encountering the Rhetorics of Exclusion in Special Education Research. *David J. Connor, Hunter College - CUNY*

Chair: *Christine Elaine Ashby, Syracuse University*

Discussant: *Hardy Murphy, Indiana University*

34.068. Statistical Frontiers: Bayesian Inference, Machine Learning, and Longitudinal Modeling. SIG-Structural

Equation Modeling and Multilevel Modeling Methods; Paper Session

InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Echo Park; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

On the Prevalence and Appropriate Use of Data-Model-Based Informative Priors for Estimating Multilevel Linear Models. *Zhigang Zhang, University of Washington; Elizabeth A. Sanders, University of Washington; Timothy R. Konold, University of Virginia*

Bayesian Piecewise Structural Equation Modeling for Interpretable Nonlinear Relations. *Dayeon Lee, University of Maryland; Gregory R. Hancock, University of Maryland*

Causal Mediation with Machine Learning Under Unmeasured Cluster-Level Confounding. *Cameron McCann, University of Texas at Austin; Xiao Liu, University of Texas at Austin*

Evaluating Cross-Lagged Models: A Comparative Analysis Using Simulated and Empirical Data. *Xiaoyu Yang, Texas A&M University; Lu Chen, Texas A&M University; Su Jiang, University of Houston Downtown; Oiman Kwok, Texas A&M University*

Targeted Machine Learning for Latent Outcomes in Causal Research. *Amota Ataneka, University of Cincinnati; Benjamin Kelcey, University of Cincinnati; Jean Baptiste Habarurema, University of Cincinnati*

Chair: *Yu-Yu Hsiao, University of New Mexico*

34.069. Advancing Meta-Analytic Methods. SIG-Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis; Paper Session

InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 6th Floor, Broadway; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Addressing Selective Reporting Bias in Meta-Analysis of Dependent Effect Sizes: A Tutorial in R. *Man Chen, University of Texas at Austin; James E. Pustejovsky, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

A Nonparametric Hyperprior for Between-studies Heterogeneity in Bayesian Meta-analysis. *Christopher G.*

Thompson, Texas A&M University

Applying Location Scale Models to Meta-Regression in Education. *Bixi Zhang, Graduate Center - CUNY; Mali Waugh, Graduate Center - CUNY; Eduardo Alarcon, Graduate Center - CUNY*

Exploring the Methodological Quality of Education Intervention Meta-Analyses: A Meta-Review. *Terri D. Pigott, Georgia State University; Marta Pellegrini, University of Cagliari; Caroline Sutton Chubb, Georgia State University; Natalie Pruitt, Georgia State University; Hannah F. Scarborough, Georgia State University*

Standardized Mean Differences: Not So Standard After All. *Juyoung Jung, University of Iowa; Ariel M. Aloe, University of Iowa*

Chair: *Man Chen, University of Texas at Austin*

34.070. Systems Thinking and Higher Education. SIG-Systems

Thinking in Education; Paper Session

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Los Cerritos; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Conceptualizing EdD Programs from a Systems Thinking Lens. *Tiina Itkonen, California State University - Channel Islands; Andrea J. Bingham, California State University - Channel Islands*

Exploring Systems Thinking as a Tool for Advancing Inquiry-Based Pedagogy in Pre-service Science Education. *Azka Kiran, Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University; Monday Moju, Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University; Lezly Taylor, Virginia Tech*

Incorporating Systems Thinking into Undergraduate Macroeconomics. *Oleg V. Pavlov, Worcester Polytechnic Institute; Natalia Smirnova, University of Connecticut; Elena V. Smirnova, SUNY - Old Westbury*

Mapping the Conceptual Terrain of Freshman and Sophomore Non-STEM Undergraduates' Knowledge of Complex Systems. *Lin Xiang, University of Kentucky; Ehimwenma S. Orobator, University of Kentucky*

Perceptions of Climate Change Plausibility through a Systems Thinking Lens: Insights from Non-Science Undergraduates. *Gizem Ozyazici, Syracuse University; Melike Hanedar, University of Maryland; Gaye D. Ceyhan, Bogazici University; John W. Tillotson, Syracuse University*

Chair: *Ryan C. Weber, Pepperdine University*

Discussant: *Lok-Sze Wong, University of North Texas*

34.071. Exploring Digital Platforms, Literacy Practices, and Pedagogical Futures from Diverse Perspectives. SIG-

Technology as an Agent of Change in Teaching and Learning; Symposium

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum C; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

The Sociality of Reading Together: How Hybrid Literacy

Infrastructures Reader's Literacies and Identities. *Maggie Bryant, Baylor University*

Mediated Practices in Connected World: Platforms as 'Sponsors of Literacy' and Youth-Led Coalitions' Relational Practices. *Rabani Garg, University of Pennsylvania*

Prompt Literacies: Investigating Cognitive Growth in AI-Supported Problem Solving. *Jongpil Cheon, Texas Tech University*

Platform Ecologies and Literacy Practices: Korean Adolescents in U.S.-Based Online Communities. *Jin Kyeong Jung, Texas Tech University*

Exploring AI for Differentiated Instructions: Preservice Teachers' Use of AI for English Language Learners. *So Lim Kim, SUNY - College at New Paltz*

Chair: *Rabani Garg, University of Pennsylvania*

Discussant: *Jin Kyeong Jung, Texas Tech University*

34.072. (Re)Shaping Our Educational Futures Through Literacies of Resistance. SIG-Writing and Literacies;

Symposium

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Atrium II; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Testimoniando Women of Color Preservice Teachers' Literacies: Reclaiming Literacies of Resistance. *Adrianna González Ybarra, The University of Texas Rio Grande Valley*

Pedagogy del Corazón: Enacting Cariño and Embedding Restorative Literacies in Postsecondary Education. *Yvette M. Regalado, University of Texas - San Antonio*

Civic Redesigns: Exploring Asian American Youths' YPAR-Based Sociopolitical Literacies of Resistance. *Ankhi Guha Thakurta, Boston College; Deepshikha Banerjee, Boston College; Yueyang Shen, Boston College*

Black Queer Youth Literacies as Maps of Resistance, Reclamation, and Revision in the Deep South. *shea wesley martin, The Ohio State University*

Chair: *monét cooper, University of Michigan*

Discussant: *Monica Gonzalez Ybarra, University of Illinois*

Division and SIG Roundtables

34.073. AERA Roundtable Session Thursday 9:45 am; Roundtable Session

34.073-1. Cultural Issues in International Curricular Framing and Materials (Table 1). Division B - Curriculum Studies;

Roundtable Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

A Critical Discourse Analysis of North Korean Defector Students' Navigation of Social Capital and Habitus in South

Korean Education. *Inui Kim, Seoul National University; Younkyung Hong, Ball State University*

An Analysis of Cultural-historically Situated Framework of National Language Competency-based Curriculum in Ethnic Taiwan. *Kai-Jung Hsiao, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Chuan-Rong Yeh, National Taichung University of Education*

Tracing Sexuality Education in Chinese Science Textbooks: A CSE-Informed Critical Discourse Analysis. *Meng Sun, East China Normal University; Junhao Zhao, East China Normal University; Sihao Xiao, East China Normal University*

Chair: *Lina Safa, Pepperdine University*

34.073-2. Conflict, Power, and Entanglements with Curriculum (Table 2). Division B - Curriculum Studies; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Could it be that power is the central problem curriculum studies should focus on? *Raul Olmo Fregoso Bailón, University of Nevada - Reno; Alfonso Arriaga Juarez, IEMS-Plantel Tláhuac II*

Conflict as a Transformational Mechanism in Education: A Philosophical Framework for Curriculum and Identity. *Anastasiia Puzyrina, Restore Connection Development Centre*

Powerful knowledge for all students: teachers as agents of recontextualisation. *Mark Hardman, Institute of Education - London; Marie Nilsberth, Karlstad University; Mikko Puustinen, University of Helsinki*

Transformative Ruptures: Advancing Social Justice through Curriculum and Pedagogy. *Brianna R. Ramirez, Glendale Community College; Ruby Osoria, California State University - San Marcos*

More than Right: Toward an Affective Curriculum of Connection. *Seth A. McCall, Lake Superior State University; Sarah M. Gerth van den Berg, Teachers College, Columbia University*

34.073-3. The Limitations of Reform: Recognizing the gaps in scripted curriculum and transformative efforts (Table 3). Division B - Curriculum Studies; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Hidden Histories: Racialized and Gendered Silences in Texas Social Studies Curriculum. *Christina Salazar, Texas Woman's University*

Imagining Just Futures: Examining Tensions Between Scripted Curriculum and the Necessity of Culturally Relevant Pedagogy. *Andrea Jamison, Illinois State University; Sara Ann Jones, Illinois State University*

Reimagining Student Agency: A Narrative Inquiry into Korean

Teachers' Struggles within a Neoliberal Education System. *Jisoo Kim, Korean Educational Development Institute; Kyounghye Seo, Ewha Womans University*

Sleeping Police in Teacher Education: The Politics of Techniques for Sensitizing Science Teachers to 'Diversity'. *Kathryn Lewkowitz Kirchgasser, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Curtis O'Dwyer, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Chair: *Maria Luisa Garcia Underwood, University of Pennsylvania*

34.073-4. Decentering the ethos of decolonial curriculum (Table 4). Division B - Curriculum Studies; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Curriculum Experiences of African Female Graduate Students in the United States and Sub-Saharan Africa. *Ernestina Wiafe, Kansas State University*

Expanding AsianCrit through Transimperial Curricular Inquiry: Korean American Ethnic Studies and the LA Uprising Lesson. *Jeong-Eun Rhee, Long Island University - C.W. Post Campus; Sohyun An, Kennesaw State University*

STEM Curriculum Development Grounded in Indigenous Knowledge and Microplastics Research. *Stacy Potes, University of Hawai'i Mānoa; Pauline W.U. Chinn, University of Hawai'i at Manoa*

We Read Aloud to Each Other: Home Languages as Aesthetic and Decolonial Openings in Teacher Education. *Cathy L. Benedict, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Chair: *Betul Ozel, University of Arizona*

34.073-5. Social Change, Social Justice (Table 5). Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

What Silence Carried: Black and Asian Solidarity as Reclamation and Refusal in Western Educational Spaces. *Darius Phelps, New York University; Diana Liu, Teachers College, Columbia University; Judy W. Yu, Boston College; David O. Beauzil, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Designed to Disrupt (the Machine): Zines as Artifacts of Personal and Disciplinary Literacies. *Omer Zahid, Vanderbilt University; Golnaz Arastoopour Irgens, Vanderbilt University*

Complicating Postcolonial Logics: Towards Transraciolinguistic Justice in Literacy Instruction. *Darshawn Patterson, University of South Florida; Patriann Smith, University of South Florida; Arlette I. Willis, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

From Margin to Multiverse: Black Speculative Feminisms and the Worldmaking of Black Girlhood in Graphic Novels.

Taryn T.C. Brown, University of Florida; Jameelah R Wright, William Paterson University; Dashana Lane, Bethune Cookman University; Deandra West, University of Florida

Chairs: *Rachelle S. Savitz, East Carolina University; Antonio L. Ellis, American University*

34.073-6. Policies, Matterings and Praxis: Research in the Social Context of Education within Schools (Table 6).

Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Kentucky Schools Perspective: The Intended Purpose for Our Next Generation. *Chelsea Blair-Richcreek, University of Louisville*

Military Recruitment in High Schools: Section 8528 of the Elementary and Secondary Education Act (ESEA). *Jaime Liborio Del Razo, Vassar College*

Reading Between the Lines: A Critical Analysis of Anti-Discrimination Policy in Greater Toronto Area Schools. *Tianna Dowie-Chin, University of Georgia; Lora Smothers, University of Georgia; D'Annette Mullen, University of Florida*

This Isn't Our School: Using Placemaking Literacies to Explore Children's Experiences After School Closure. *Kristin Valle Geren, University of South Florida*

Teacher Influencers Discuss AI Digital Textbooks: A TPACK Analysis of South Korean T-Tubers. *Seun Jeon, University of Minnesota*

Chair: *Elvira Pichardo, Lewis University*

34.073-7. The Relationship of Climate and Belonging with STEM (Table 7). SIG-School Community, Climate, and Culture; Roundtable Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Exploring School STEM Climate and Students' Science Attitudes and Interests: A Multi-Level Analysis of TIMSS 2019. *Xin Xia, University of Georgia*

How Do I Belong Compared With Others? Relative Belonging and Math Achievement in Chinese Adolescents. *Yushan Zhao, University of California - Davis; Kevin A. Gee, University of California - Davis; Caleb Wang Yuan, University of Arizona*

Unpacking the Interaction Between Teacher Experience and Student-teacher Relationships in Predicting Early Math Achievement. *Amanda Olsen, University of Missouri; Rachel Min Wong, University of Tennessee*

34.073-8. Towards A Politics of Multiplicity: Reimagining the Future of "Ensemble" in Art and Education (Table 8).

SIG-Arts and Inquiry in the Visual and Performing Arts in Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Rehearsing the Anthropocene: Devised Theatre Praxis for Collective Embodied Sensemaking. *Lana Cosic, Vanderbilt University*

A Patchwork of Witness: More-Than-Human Ensembles. *Anastasia Y. Goodwin, Vanderbilt University*

Rehearsing Alternative Futures for Sex Education: Embracing the Unknowing of Collaborative Meaning-Making. *Amanda Harris, University of California - Los Angeles*

Creative Collaboration Across Differences: Ensemble Work for Abolition. *Cassidy L. Martin, University of Southern California*

Discussant: *Lora Cawelti, University of Southern California*

34.073-9. Unforgetting as Pedagogy: Reclaiming Histories and Reimagining Futures in Education (Table 9). SIG-Critical Issues in Curriculum and Cultural Studies; Roundtable Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Pedagogy as Reckoning: Ethics and Futures in the Teaching of Disciplinary Knowledge. *Francisco Medina, John Jay College of Criminal Justice*

Reimagining Psychology With and Against AI: Using ChatGPT as a Pedagogical Partner. *Marjorine Henriquez-Castillo, Lehman College - CUNY*

Decolonization and Rehumanizing Mathematics in Teacher Education: Sensing New Relations. *Atasi Das, Lehman College - CUNY*

Fugitive Kid Curricula: Unforgetting Children's Acts of Learning Beyond Adult Control. *Kushya Sugarman, Mount Holyoke College*

Chair: *Francisco Medina, John Jay College of Criminal Justice*

Discussant: *Marjorine Henriquez-Castillo, Lehman College - CUNY*

34.073-10. Transnational Insights on Decolonial Education (Table 10). SIG-Decolonial, Postcolonial, and Anti-Colonial Studies in Education; Roundtable Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Decentering the West: A Transnational Analysis of Settler-Colonial Education in Turkey, Japan, and Brazil. *Levon Ghanimian, Claremont Graduate University*

Decolonial Critiques of the South Korean K-12 Curriculum: A Scoping Review. *JEONGMIN SEO, Seoul National University; Sung-Sang Yoo, Seoul National University*

Japanese International Initiative and Its Reproduction of Global

Racial Hierarchy Within Global Coloniality. *Satomi Mitani, University of Minnesota*

The Language of Access: How English shapes admissions to South Africa's Universities of Technology. *Lyndall E. Kemm-Stols, Durban University of Technology*

China's "Ecological Civilization" as Alternative Ethico-Onto-Episteme to Radicalize Global Sustainability Education?: Flashpoints and New Imaginaries. *Weili Zhao, Hangzhou Normal University*

Chair: *Fatima Seyma Kizil, Syracuse University*

34.074. AERA Roundtable Session Thursday 9:45 am;
Roundtable Session

34.074-1. Raciolinguistics and Intersectionality in Language Education (Table 1). SIG-Bilingual Education Research; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Empowering Future Bilingual Teachers through Teaching Science in Spanish in an Undergraduate Service-Learning Program. *Perla Ramos Carranza, California Polytechnic State University - San Luis Obispo; Jasmine M. Nation, California Polytechnic State University - San Luis Obispo; Alejandra Yep, California Polytechnic State University - San Luis Obispo; Dayana Limon Limon Santiago, Cal Poly, San Luis Obispo; Citlali Luna Silva, Cal Poly, San Luis Obispo*

Engaging Teacher Candidates with Critical Multilingual Language Awareness and Anti-Racist Translanguaging through the PeCK-LIT Test. *Shakina Rajendram, University of Toronto; Jennifer L. Burton, Concordia University*

My Drive to Communicate: A Mixed-Methods Case Study on Pre-Service Bilingual Teachers' Willingness to Communicate. *Paulina Chapa, University of Texas at Austin*

Navigating Multilingual Classrooms in Teacher Education: Development of Teacher Identity for Monolingual and Bilingual Candidates. *Cesar Pena-Sandoval, Universidad Metropolitana de Ciencias de la Educación; Renee Shank, University of Washington; Teddi M. Beam-Conroy, University of Washington*

Negotiating Language, Race, and Identity: Action Research with Pre-Service ESL Teachers' Critical Practice. *Jennifer L. Burton, Concordia University; Aya Ceilidh Halliday, Concordia University - Montreal*

34.074-2. Reimagining Programs and Curricular Practices in Dual Language Education (Table 2). SIG-Bilingual Education Research; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Reimagining Place as a Critical Theory Tenet in Rural Dual Language Immersion Programs. *Maria R. Coady, North*

Carolina State University; Maria Heysha Carrillo Carrasquillo, North Carolina State University; Joanna Koch, North Carolina State University; Zaina Dali, North Carolina State University; Cassandra Rubinstein, North Carolina State University; Alejandro Amaya, North Carolina State University; Rocío López Caicedo, North Carolina State University

Student Linguistic Agency in DLBE Classrooms: Contextual Considerations. *Maria Auxiliadora Cerrato, Georgia State University; Lisa Domke, Georgia State University*

The Impact of Dual Language Immersion on High School Outcomes. *Manuel Vazquez, Education Northwest*

A Space for Translanguaging: Secondary Students' Agency and Identity Construction in Multilingual Online Classroom Discussions. *Hannah Park, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Jiaxuan Zong, University of Maryland; Nihat Polat, University of Maryland*

Sphota and the Bilingual Mind: Reimagining Translanguaging Beyond Structure and Fluidity. *Gautam Singh Bisht, Northwestern University*

34.074-3. Reviews of Literature and Scholarship (Table 3). SIG-Research on Women and Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Mapping Historical and Evolving Narratives in Women's Leadership Research Over 25 Years. *Beverly J. Irby, Texas A&M University; Nahed Abdelrahman, The University of Southern Mississippi; Jordan Donop, Texas A&M University; Julia Nell Ballenger, East Texas A&M University; Sonia Rodriguez, National University; Kristina Hall, Texas A&M University; Rebecca Philips, Texas A&M University; Cynthia Angélica Gallardo, Texas A&M International University*

Impact of Dialogic Feminist Gatherings on Teacher Training for Gender Equality: A Literature Review. *Sara Carbonell, University of Valencia; Esther Roca Campos, University of Valencia; Guillermo Legorburo-Torres, University Rovira i Virgili*

Depicting Inequality: A Scoping Review of Material Metaphors Describing Racialized and Gendered Career Differences. *Lauren P. Bailes, University of Delaware; Yubin Jang, University of Delaware*

34.074-4. Contemporary Issues In Education (Table 4). SIG-International Studies; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Title: Bridging Divides: Language, Identity, and the Integration Challenges of Arab Female Teachers in Jewish Educational Institutions. *Eman Abo-Zaed Arar, Texas State University*

Between Aspirations and Policies: How Families, Schools, and the State Define Generation Z's Pathways in Türkiye. *Gulcin Aslan, Eskisehir Osmangazi University; Hamit Ozen, Eskisehir Osmangazi University; Eman Abo-Zaed Arar, Texas State University; Khalid Husny Arar, Texas State University*

Building Community and Other Ways of Knowing: Competences in a Global, Collaborative Informal Learning Environment. *Danielle Pascual Espino, Pepperdine University; Kristina M. Lux, Pepperdine University/Newport Healthcare; Seung B. Lee, Pepperdine University; Eric R. Hamilton, Pepperdine University*

High-Stakes, Uneven Ground: English Proficiency Across School Types in Costa Rica. *Jose Fabian Elizondo-Gonzalez, University of Kansas; Walter Araya Garita, Universidad de Costa Rica; Ana Carolina González Ramirez, Universidad de Costa Rica*

From Elitism to Equity?: Discursive Recontextualization of the International Baccalaureate in South Korea's Public Education Reform. *Hyungryeol Kim, Seoul National University*

Chair: *Dion Burns, Learning Policy Institute*

34.074-5. Policy, Language, and Educational Transformation in the Caribbean (Table 5). SIG-Caribbean and African Studies in Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Investigating Educational Attainment Pertaining to E-Health Literacy and Acceptance in the Dominican Republic. *Salenah Cartier, University of Houston; Arianna Colon, University of Houston; Daisy Contreras, University of Houston; Sujaira Garza, University of Houston; Monica Adams, University of Houston*

Reimagining Quality Secondary Education: Community Voices from the BVI. *Anica G. Bowe, Rutgers University - Newark; Jasmattie Yamraj, H. Lavity Stouff Community College*

Saint Lucia's National Language Policy of 2018: A Discourse analysis. *Hector Rafael Castrillon-Costa, University of Texas - San Antonio*

Teaching AI Literacy through Caribbean Eyes: Cultural Contexts in Image Generation. *Stephanie Bent, University of Maryland*

Chair: *Alicia Francisca Noreiga, Acadia University*

34.074-6. Critical Examination of Race, Ethnicity, Class, and Gender Roundtable: [Dis]Ability Injustice and the Disproportionality in School Discipline (Table 6). SIG-Critical Examination of Race, Ethnicity, Class and Gender in Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

A QuantCrit Analysis of Discipline Outcomes for Girls Receiving Special Education. *Lynette O'Neal, Texas A&M University; Kristian Edosomwan, University of Houston*

Dismantling [dis]ability injustice: Exploring the impact of virtual learning on students with disabilities and subsequent human rights violations in U.S. schools. *Timmesha Butler-Davis, Ramapo College; Marcia J. Watson-Vandiver, Towson University; Deneen S. Dixon-Payne, Towson University*

A Profile Analysis of Districts Cited for Significant Disproportionality in Texas. *Katherine A. Graves, Utah State University; Ambra Green, University of Texas - Arlington; Megan Meredith, University of Texas - Arlington; Kelvin Tosin Afolabi, University of Texas at Arlington; Janine Shuman, University of Texas - Arlington*

Chair: *Tamara Handy, Teachers College, Columbia University*

34.074-7. Rest as an Extraordinary Literacy: Black Women Educators Reclaiming Power Through Stillness, Silence, Silliness, and Refusal (Table 7). SIG-Critical Examination of Race, Ethnicity, Class and Gender in Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Sabbath Pedagogies as Extraordinary Literacies: Disrupting Black Women Grind Culture Through Sacred Pacing. *Azaria I. Cunningham, Boston University*

Dreaming in the Wake: Afrofuturist Remedies for White Supremacist Patriarchal Encounters in Higher Education. *Wideline Seraphin, University of Texas - Arlington*

Rest as Resistance: A Redefinition of Being, Doing, Work, and Stillness. *Phoebe Quaynor, Pennsylvania State University*

How Does It Hurt?: Black Women Leaders in Higher Ed and the Extraordinary Literacies of Rest, Refusal, and Inner Reclamation. *Nakisha D. Whittington, Stanford University*

Integrating Extraordinary Literacies And Rest Rituals Into Science Teacher Education: Teaching From The Nap Ministry. *Jennifer Jackson, Oak Ridge Institute for Science and Education*

The Ways Rest Heals The Matrix Of Oppressions: How Silence, Stillness, and Silliness Function As Extraordinary Literacies. *Jeanine M. Staples-Dixon, Pennsylvania State University*

Chair: *Janice A. Byrd, Pennsylvania State University*

34.074-8. Unforgetting Histories and Imagining Futures: Indigenous Narratives in Education Research (Table 8). SIG-Indigenous Peoples of the Pacific and Beyond; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Huaka'i nui, huaka'i 'iki: Transformative journeys on 'āina and

in ourselves. *Dawn Rego-Yee, Ceeds of Peace; Kekoa Rosehill, Hālau 'Ōhi'a*

Kūkulu Ea: Indigenous Research Tools for Rebuilding More Sovereign Futures. *Julie L. Kaomea, University of Hawai'i at Manoa*

Unforgetting Histories and Imagining Futures: The Lives and Times of Children Educated under the New Zealand Native Schools Act. *Margaret J. Maaka, University of Hawai'i at Manoa; Ivy Kahukiwa Smith, Te Kōpere o te Iwi o Hineuru*

Wāhine Toa: Unforgetting Histories and Reimagining Futures of Women's Leadership in the Hineuru Iwi context. *Teracia Smith, Tamatea Pōkai Whenua (Trust)*

Chair: *Richard Walk, University of Hawai'i at Mānoa*

Discussant: *H. Ka'umealani K. Walk, Kula Kaiapuni Hawai'i 'o Kahuku Academy, HIDOE*

34.074-9. Reimagining Belonging: Latinx and AfroLatiné Resistance, Identity, and Persistence Across Educational Spaces (Table 9). SIG-Latina/o/x Research Issues; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

The Role of Culture Centers for Multiracial Latinx Students. *Sylvia Martinez, Indiana University*

Understanding Chronic Absenteeism Among Latino High School Students: Uncovering Root Causes Beyond. *Paola Suchsland, California State University - Fullerton; Sally Jarvis-Lubbe, California State University - Fullerton*

Latino Men's Vertical Transfer Outcomes and Experiences in the Nuevo South. *Carmen Serrata, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Sandra L. Dika, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Onima Vadakke Thodiyil, University of North Carolina - Charlotte*

I Play, Therefore I Am: Sounding AfroLatiné Identity Through Cultural Musics. *Marjoris V. Regus, Rutgers University*

Chair: *Sylvia Martinez, Indiana University*

34.075. AERA Roundtable Session Thursday 9:45 am - Gold 1; Roundtable Session

34.075-1. Roundtable 1 (Table 1). Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Financial Aid Roller Coasting: An Estimation of Losing and Regaining the HOPE Grant on Academic Outcomes. *Manuel S. Gonzalez Canche, University of Pennsylvania; Youning Zhao, Michigan State University; Feifan Shan, University of Pennsylvania*

Forecasting Long-Run Effects of College Interventions Using Short-Term Impacts. *Mindy Lachs Rosengarten, Teachers College, Columbia University; Drew Bailey, University of*

California - Irvine; Michael Joseph Weiss, MDRC; Tyler Watts, Teachers College, Columbia University

Bridging the Gap: Income-Based Disparities in Career Preparedness and the Role of Collegiate Experiences. *Wonki Lee, University of California - Los Angeles; Casey Shapiro, University of California - Los Angeles; Elena Peterson, University of California - Los Angeles; Valeria G. Dominguez, University of California - Los Angeles; Erin O'Leary, University of California - Los Angeles; Kem Saichaie, University of California, Los Angeles*

Chair: *Brian An, University of Iowa*

34.075-2. Non-Instructional Staff at Postsecondary Institutions (Table 2). Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Beyond Simple Ratios: Using Elastic Net Regression to Model Noninstructional Staffing at AAU Institutions. *Mahmut Gundogdu, Texas A&M University; Elif Aslaner, Claremont Graduate University; Hasan Aydin, Florida Gulf Coast University*

From Faculty-Centric to Institution-Wide: Expanding Mentorship in Higher Education for Women Staff. *Angela Clark-Taylor, St. John Fisher University; Emily Thatcher Creamer, The Ohio State University; Susan V. Iverson, Manhattanville University*

It's Always Sunny in Academia: A Mixed Methods Study of Workplace Bullying of University Staff. *Tara Burke, University of Arizona*

The Impact of External Compensated Mentorship on Career Advancement for Women in Athletic Administration. *Kelly Britsky, Andrew College; Michael Lanford, University of North Georgia*

Chair: *Kelly S. Hall, Texas A&M University - Kingsville*

34.075-3. Division J Section 6: Roundtable 2 (Table 3). Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

American University as Tensegrity: In-between Decolonization and Internationalization. *Jonggeun Park, Teachers College, Columbia University; Dani Friedrich, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Crisis, Compliance, and Care: Institutional Belonging and International Student Mobility in U.S. Higher Education. *Haishan Yang, University of Southern California; Sanfeng Miao, Michigan State University*

Gendered Labor Exploitation and the Reproduction of Inequity: Structural Conditions Shaping Higher Education. *Madeline Michelle Weiler, University of Dayton*

34.075-4. Preparing Educators for Complex Classrooms: Integration, Leadership, and Content Challenges Across Disciplines (Table 4). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- Enhancing Integrated STEM Instruction Through Teacher Professional Development: A Systematic Review. *Blessed Aspinas Mhungu, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Desiree Nosipho Cele, University at Buffalo - SUNY*
- From Problem Inflation to Intellectual Leadership: Constructing Math Teacher Candidates to Solve Real Educational Problems in the Age of Social Media. *Antoinette S. Linton, California State University - Fullerton; Cherie Ichinose, California State University - Fullerton*
- Incomplete Integration: A Systematic Literature Review of Secondary Engineering Instructional Practices within Classroom Settings. *Erica Cheva, Florida Atlantic University*
- Teaching War: A Literature Review of Secondary Social Studies Teachers. *Jonathan Lancaster, Montclair State University*
- Factors Influencing Pre-Service Teachers' Integration of Artificial Intelligence in Mathematics Education. *Hea-Jin Lee, The Ohio State University - Lima*
- Chair: *Jonathan Lancaster, Montclair State University*

34.075-5. Teaching Lives in China: Pathways, Responsibilities, and Renewal (Table 5). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- External input and internal generation: the Chinese experience of how urban retired teachers maximize support for impoverished rural schools. *Hao Cheng, Central China Normal University; Qiqi Zhang, Central China Normal University; Zhiping Mai, Central China Normal University; Hongfeng Yang, Wuhan Institute of Technology*
- From Formative Experience to Teaching Practice: Chinese Elementary Teachers' Career Choice and Student Relationship Building. *Yijing Zhang, University of Maryland; Chunru Dong, University of Maryland*
- Taking on Greater Responsibilities: Understanding the Role of Local Teachers in International Schools in China. *Chen Zhao, University of Cambridge*
- Chair: *Qiqi Zhang, Central China Normal University*

34.075-6. Algorithms of Power: AI, Policy, and the Future of Education (Table 6). Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- Are Teacher Preparation Programs in Higher Education Ready for the AI Era? A Comparative Analysis of AI Policies for Teachers and Learners in China, the U.S., and Norway. *Jialin Yan, University of Rochester; Nicole King, University of Rhode Island; Anne Øgreid, oslo metropolitan university; Harald Eriksen, oslo metropolitan university*
- Bridging the AI Equity Gap: Unfunded Mandates and Teacher Resistance. *Ban Wang, HONG KONG UNIVERSITY; Paul Campbell, The University of Hong Kong*
- Initial Moves: Teachers Navigating AI Integration in a Policy Vacuum. *Anderson Neal de Andrade, Rutgers University*
- Unencumbered Innovation? Industry Influence and Ethical Tensions in GenAI Policy in a Midwestern State. *Ali Raza, Grand Valley State University; Stefanie L. Marshall, Michigan State University*
- Unforgetting Policy Failures: Technosocial Scotomas in Historical and Contemporary Data Initiatives. *Edward Dieterle, Education Research Partners, LLC*
- Discussant: *Amanda U. Potterton, University of Kentucky*

34.075-7. From Authorship to Algorithm: Rethinking Policy, Integrity, and Academic Publishing in the AI Era (Table 7). Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- A Comparative Study of the Governance of AIED Ethical Issues through Policy Text Mining. *SIQI WANG, University of Edinburgh*
- A Critical Discourse Analysis of R-1 University Website on AI and Environmental Responsibility. *Saesaem Yoon, University of Washington - Tacoma; Jason Litzenberg, Pennsylvania State University*
- Authorship, Integrity, and AI: How Academic Publishers Are Responding to Generative Artificial Intelligence. *Azadeh Hassani, University of Nebraska - Lincoln; Guy Trainin, University of Nebraska - Lincoln; Shuling Yang, University of Maryland - Baltimore County; Carin L. Applegate, Creighton University*
- Generative Artificial Intelligence Policies and Guidelines at Flagship Public Universities in the United States. *Jason LaFrance, Appalachian State University*
- Institutional Responsiveness to Global Education Policy: A Bibliometric Analysis of Generative AI Research and SDG4 (2023-June 2025). *Ari Jiayu An, Stanford University; Shuman Wang, Stanford University*
- Chair: *Shahin Hossain, University of Maryland - Baltimore County*

34.075-8. Comparing Classrooms: International Views on Teacher Job Satisfaction and Practice (Table 8). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Comparing Teacher Job Satisfaction in Australia, Canada, UK,
and US: Evidence from TALIS 2018. *Xumei Fan, University
of Northern Iowa*

Exploring (De)Motivating Factors over Time: Perspectives of
Career Change STEM Teachers from Germany and Israel.
*Ainat Guberman, David Yellin College of Education;
Gabriela Jonas-Ahrend, Paderborn University; Rinat Arviv
Elyashiv, Kibbutzim College of Education; Gal Ben-
Yehudah, The Open University of Israel; Dominik Cyrus,
Paderborn University*

Pre-service English Teachers' Translanguaging Practices in
Hong Kong Secondary School Classrooms: An Activity
Theory Perspective. *Hanyun Wu, University of Hong Kong*

Chair: *Ainat Guberman, David Yellin College of Education*

34.076. AERA Roundtable Session Thursday 9:45 am - Gold 2;
Roundtable Session

**34.076-1. Fostering High Quality Early Learning Instruction
for Dual Language Learners through Classroom
Observation Research (Table 1).** SIG-Classroom
Observation; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Sharpening the focus: Using domain-specific tools for coaching
to improve classroom quality for DLLs. *Alexandra
Figueras-Daniel, National Institute for Early Education
Research; Christina Stephens, National Institute for Early
Education Research*

Examining Language Supports for Dual Language Learners
(DLLs) in Transitional Kindergarten Classrooms Using the
COLES-DLL. *Lisa Jean White, American Institutes for
Research; Leanne Elliott, American Institutes for Research*

Developing and Piloting an Observation Tool for Multilingual
Learners in Preschool and Kindergarten Classrooms.
*Camille Whitney, Sobrato Early Academic Language
(SEAL); Martha Irene Martinez, SEAL; Guadalupe Diaz
Lara, California State University - Fullerton*

Chair: *Martha Irene Martinez, SEAL*

Discussant: *Claudia Rodriguez-Mojica, University of California -
Davis*

34.076-2. Family and Parent Engagement (Table 2). SIG-Early
Education and Child Development; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Family-Centered Approaches to Supporting Kindergarten
Transitions at a Preschool in Hawai'i. *Taryn Ashlee
Nakagawa, University of Hawaii - Manoa*

"Smart" Nudges, Real Gains: Family Engagement for
Kindergarten Math Readiness. *Anastasia L. Betts,
Learnology Labs; Benjamin Ryon, Learnology; Elida V.
Laski, Boston College*

Family Engagement as Pathway to Equity? Racial and
Linguistic Differences in Head Start Children's Outcomes.
Yijie Wang, University of Washington

Exploring the experiences and expertise of Early Care and
Learning Professionals to develop tools to support families
with young children experiencing homelessness and/or
housing insecurity. *Katherine Kresin Delaney, University of
Toledo*

The Anatomy of "Sticky Chats": Identifying and Disrupting
Five Addictive Interaction Patterns in Child-AI
Conversations (Poster 27). *Sonia Tiwari, Kids AI; Jennifer J.
Chen, Kean University*

Parental Satisfaction with Child Care under Canada's Low-Cost
Policy: A Thematic and LLM-Based Analysis. *Esther Yu,
University of Toronto - OISE; Yunqi Xie, University of
Toronto - OISE; Samantha Burns, University of Guelph; Joel
Wiebe, University of Toronto - OISE; Jesseca Perlman,
University of Toronto - OISE; Michal Perlman, University of
Toronto - OISE*

Chair: *Anastasia L. Betts, Learnology Labs*

**34.076-3. Social-Emotional Development and Regulation
(Table 3).** SIG-Early Education and Child Development;
Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Profiling Preschoolers' Social-Emotional Behaviors and Their
Academic Outcomes in China. *Jing Li, The Chinese
University of Hong Kong; Barry Bai, Chinese University of
Hong Kong; Hongfang Li, Baicao Yuan Kindergarten;
Qiuyun Chen, Jiabaotian kindergarten; Qin Ji, Qingxiu
kindergarten*

English Language and Social-Emotional Skills of Preschool-
Aged Children: Profiles, Home Linguistic Environments,
and School Readiness. *Jun Wang, The Ohio State University;
Rachel Hur, Johns Hopkins University; Lieny Jeon,
University of Virginia*

Understanding the Pathways Between ACEs and Early Social-
Emotional Development: A National SEM Study. *Chin-Chih
Chen, Virginia Commonwealth University; Fa Zhang, Open
University of China; Yaoying Xu, Virginia Commonwealth
University; Yuyan Xia, University of Kentucky; Jamie L.
Cage, Virginia Commonwealth University*

Early Elementary Classroom Climate Universally Predicting
Academic Gains Through Gains in Social-emotional Skills.
*Nan Xiao, University of California, Irvine; Kimberly R. M.
Osborne, Arizona State University; Sabina Low, Arizona
State University*

Emotion Regulation Strategy Knowledge and Social-Emotional

Skills in Early Childhood: Linking Self-Reports to Teacher Ratings. *Catie Connolly, Stanford University; Emma Strouse, Stanford University; Jelena Obradovic, Stanford University*

Chair: *Nan Xiao, University of California, Irvine*

34.076-4. Linguistic Justice and Heritage Education (Table 4).

SIG-Multicultural/Multiethnic Education: Theory, Research and Practice; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Linguistic Justice Through Storytelling: Multilingual Voices in Academic Spaces. *Maria Elizabeth Garza, Stony Brook University - SUNY; Joy Janzen, Stony Brook University - SUNY*

Supporting Culturally, Linguistically, Economically Diverse Learners in Gifted and Talented Programs. *Camille Austin Henderson, Texas Christian University*

Supporting Heritage Speakers of Spanish by Unforgetting No-Child-Left-Behind: Mediating Linguistic (In)Security Through Multilingual Education. *Scarlet Peterson, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Chair: *Huanshu Yuan, Marshall University*

34.076-5. Transformative Curricula and Student

Empowerment (Table 5). SIG-Multicultural/Multiethnic Education: Theory, Research and Practice; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

From Access to Affirmation: The Transformative Benefits of Ethnic Studies on Transfer Students at a Minority-Serving Institution. *Chang Wang, University of California - Santa Barbara*

From Awareness to Action: Multicultural Literature as a Tool for Inclusive, Cross-Cultural Teacher Preparation. *Elsie Solis, California State University - San Marcos; Nirmala Griarte Flores, California State Polytechnic University - Pomona; Isabel Badilla Zamora, Universidad Nacional of Costa Rica*

Toward Equity-Centered STEAM Talent Development: Reconceptualizing Opportunities for Culturally and Linguistically Diverse Learners. *Emma H. Cho, University of Washington*

Chair: *Cheng Chang, Binghamton University - SUNY*

34.076-6. Investigating the Experiences of Students, Teachers, and Coaches in Early Childhood Mathematics (Table 6).

SIG-Research in Mathematics Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Children's Visual-Numerical Reasoning in Partitioning: A Framework Grounded in Gestalt and Scheme Theories. *Maryam Zolfaghari, Kent State University; Hadi Rahmati, Kent State University; Karl W. Kosko, Kent State University*
“¿De qué otra forma lo podemos hacer?” The elevation of cognitive demand in preschool. *Nicholas C. Johnson, San Diego State University; Carlos Alejandro de Alba, San Diego State University*

Math Coaching Practices in Early Childhood and Elementary Education: A Systematic Review. *Isabelle Eng, University of Michigan*

Student Engagement in an Advanced Mathematics Program: A Case Study of Young Gifted English Learners. *Jenny Yang, St. John's University; Gulnur Ozbek, St. John's University; Vinh Quang Tran, St. John's University; Seokhee Cho, St. John's University*

“Who Am I?”: How Do Young Children Represent Their (Mathematical) Identities? *Dawn Woods, Oakland University; Fei Xu, Oakland University*

Chair: *Rupam Saran, Medgar Evers College - CUNY*

34.076-7. Research-Practice Partnerships as Engines of Innovation: Supporting Leaders and Teachers (Table 7).

SIG-School-University Partnership Research; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Developing an ECE-based research-practice partnership for educational leadership development and knowledge sharing in Los Angeles. *Allison Mattheis, California State University - Los Angeles; James Goodrich, California State University - Los Angeles; Katia Barone, California State University - Los Angeles; Vanessa Perez, California State University - Los Angeles; Janaina Maudonnet, California State University - Los Angeles; Jorge Ramirez, Pacific Oaks College*

Navigating Complexities of Co-design: Researchers' Insights from a Translanguaging-Focused Science Professional Development. *Araceli Enriquez-Andrade, University of Houston; Mimi Miyoung Lee, University of Houston; Haemin Kim, University of Houston; Jie Zhang, University of Houston*

Discussant: *Janna Dresden, University of Georgia*

34.077. AERA Roundtable Session Thursday 9:45 am - Gold 4;
Roundtable Session

34.077-1. Bridging Campuses, Communities, and Classrooms: Collaborative Pathways to Lasting Change (Table 1).

SIG-School, University, Community Collaborative Research; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Expanding Mental Health Access in Rural Schools Through School-University Partnerships. *Kathleen Provinzano, Binghamton University - SUNY; Connor J. Sondergeld, MetriKs; Eleanor Churchland, MetriKs; Casey E Hanna, Binghamton University - SUNY; Toni A. May, Binghamton University - SUNY; Naorah Rimkunas, Binghamton University - SUNY; Kelley Cook, Binghamton University - SUNY*

Strengthening Communities through Place-Based University Partnerships. *Prajakt Pande, Aarhus University; Marc Sager, Southern Methodist University; Karen Pierce, Southern Methodist University; Jessica Murillo, Southern Methodist University; Rolanda Washington, Southern Methodist University*

How Practitioners Approach Equity-Focused Leadership in a Community School Context. *Casey E Hanna, Binghamton University - SUNY; Kathleen Provinzano, Binghamton University - SUNY; Eleanor Churchland, MetriKs; Toni A. May, Binghamton University - SUNY*

Community Engaged Humanizing Pedagogy: Enactment in a University-District Partnership & Implications. *Maria del Carmen Salazar, University of Denver; Nadia Alma Saldaña-Spiegle, University of Denver*

Chair: *Christopher E. Darby, ARE-LO Strategies*

34.077-2. Innovations and Evidence-Based Perspectives in Literacy Instruction, Learning, and Research (Table 2).

Division C - Learning and Instruction; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

A Computational Approach for Assessing Quantitative Aspects of Multiple-Text Integration Using Text Mining Techniques. *SeongYeup Kim, Pennsylvania State University; Rayne A. Sperling, Pennsylvania State University*

Optimizing Graphic Organizers for L2 Learning: Effects of Timing and Interactivity. *Min Huang, Texas Tech University; Jongpil Cheon, Texas Tech University; Feliza Marie Mercado, Texas Tech University; Xuan He, Texas Tech University; Masoud Askarnia, Texas Tech University*

The Role of Discussion-Based Pedagogies in Promoting Multiple-Text Learning: A Systematic Review. *Yue Tang, Pennsylvania State University; P. Karen Murphy, Pennsylvania State University; Rachel Miriam Vriend Croninger, Pennsylvania State University*

Trends in Early Literacy Instructional Practices (2006-2023): A Systematic Literature Review. *Kindel Turner Nash, Appalachian State University; Debra Prykanowski, Appalachian State University; Peijuan Cao, Appalachian State University; Gretchen Robinson, North Carolina A&T State University; Rebecca Payne Jordan, Salem College; Ashley Pennell, Appalachian State University; Aftynne E. Cheek, Appalachian State University; Jennifer Jaramillo,*

The Early Childhood Group; Woodrow R. Trathen, Appalachian State University

34.077-3. Language and Literacy Development in Multilingual Contexts (Table 3). Division C - Learning and Instruction; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Cross-Language Transfer of Reading Comprehension: A Meta-Analysis of Correlational Strength and Moderators. *Xizi Zhang, University of California - Los Angeles; Alison L. Bailey, University of California - Los Angeles*

Executive Functions, Decoding, and Oral Language: English Reading in Low-Income Immigrant Chinese-English Dual Language Learners. *Emily Mak, Texas A&M University; Lu Yang, Yangtze University; Qing Zhou, University of California - Berkeley; Yuuko Uchikoshi, University of California - Davis*

Intentional Language Teaching and Early Chinese Language Development: A Longitudinal Multilevel Study. *Yongjia Yu, University of Hong Kong; Carrie Lau, University of Hong Kong*

Literacy Skills and Learning Opportunities for Dual Language Learners and English-Only Students in Early Grades. *Jin Kyoung Hwang, University of California - Irvine; Ashley Sanabria, San Diego State University; Deborah Lowe Vandell, University of California, Irvine*

Longitudinal Relations of Spanish-English Bilingual Spelling: Influences of Spelling Scoring Method and Instructional Programs. *Youngsun Moon, Stanford University; Young-Suk Grace Kim, University of California - Irvine*

Chair: *Sandra Barrueco, The Catholic University of America*

34.077-4. Speculative Space: A Conversational Laboratory to Explore Speculative Education and Research in the Professions (Table 4). Division I - Education in the Professions; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

A Speculative Worldview to Make Sense of Complexity. *Tiffany Chambers, University of California - San Francisco*
From Strangeness to Speculation: Linguistic Tools Defamiliarizing the Present to Imagine the Future. *Abigail W. Konopasky, Dartmouth College*

Speculative Space: Radical Imagining of Spatial Justice in Education in the Professions. *Darrell D. Jackson, University of Wyoming*

Into the Nepantla: Visions of Racially and Ethnically Marginalized Disabled Medical Students. *Hannah L. Kakara Anderson, Maastricht University*

Chair: *Bridget Colleen O'Brien, University of California - San Francisco*

34.077-5. AI and Instructional Design (Table 5). SIG-Instructional Technology; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Instructional Design Students' Intention to Use AI Tools in ID Practices. *Ying Chen, Syracuse University; Moon-Heum Cho, Syracuse University*

Exploring How Instructional Designers Use AI: A Case Study in Graduate-Level Instructional Design Course. *Hyeseong Kwon, Seoul National University; Keunjae Kim, Oklahoma State University; Kyungwook Jeong, Seoul National University; Cheolil Lim, Seoul National University*

A Systematic Review of Instruments and Frameworks for Measuring Faculty AI Integration Knowledge, Attitudes, and Behaviors in Higher Education. *Richard Dickson Amoako, University of Tennessee; Jennifer A. Morrow, University of Tennessee*

Designing a Cross-Disciplinary Rubric for Assessing Preservice Teachers' Applied Technology Integration Competencies. *Rebecca M. Clark-Stallkamp, East Carolina University; Crisiane Berry, East Carolina University; Bethann Fine-Cole, East Carolina University; Xi Lin, East Carolina University*

Chair: *Nesma Ragab Nasr, Northern Arizona University*

34.077-6. Roundtable: Informal Learning Practices in the Learning Sciences (Table 6). SIG-Learning Sciences; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

A Call for Research on Contingent Trust to Support Data and Information Literacy. *Iris Tabak, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev; Ilana Dubovi, Tel Aviv University; Josh L. Radinsky, University of Illinois at Chicago*

Assigning Roles in Educational Escape Rooms for Nursing Students- Effective or Not? *Seungjie Clarice Han, Florida State University; Chaewon Kim, Florida State University; Brooke Evans, Florida State University; Lana Lipscomb, Florida State University*

Life Transitions and Making: An Exploratory Study of Older Adults from a Library Program on the Maker Movement. *Hyewon Park, University of California - Davis; Yong Ju Jung, University of Oklahoma; Ellen Rubenstein, University of Oklahoma*

Designing Chatbots to Support Self-Regulated Learning and Systems Thinking. *Saerok Park, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Ha Nguyen, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Jie Cao, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*

34.077-7. Motivational Perspectives on Emotions and Mental

Health (Table 7). SIG-Motivation in Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

A Within- and Between-Person Investigation on How Control-Value Appraisals Shape Math Anxiety Development. *Tianyu Li, Austin Peay State University; Jiawei Xiong, Curriculum Associates; Zhe Wang, Texas A&M University; Kyra Foley, Texas A&M University; Minchao Wang, Texas A&M University*

Learning Avoidance Mediates the Longitudinal Effects of Math Anxiety on Math Achievement Development. *Kyra Foley, Texas A&M University; Tianyu Li, Austin Peay State University; Minchao Wang, Texas A&M University; Zhe Wang, Texas A&M University*

The Art of Emotion Regulation: Medical Students' Emotion Regulation Behavior Towards an Upcoming Exam. *Tanja Bross, University of Augsburg; Nadja Karossa, University of Augsburg; Thomas Rothhoff, University of Augsburg; Ann-Kathrin Schindler, University of Augsburg; Sarah Junginger, University of Augsburg; Markus Dresel, University of Augsburg; Ingo Kollar, University of Augsburg; Ulrike Elisabeth Nett, Augsburg University*

When Learning Feels Impossible: A Scoping Review of Academic Motivation and Student Mental Health. *Charlotte A. Agger, Indiana University; Jack Komer, Indiana University; Heather Ormiston, Indiana University; Elizabeth McPherson, Indiana University*

Chair: *David B. Miele, Boston College*

34.077-8. Talk the Talk: Centering Dialogue in Methodology (Table 8). SIG-Qualitative Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Roleplay and Real Talk: Toward a Table-Talk Gaming Methodology. *Samantha Silberstein, University of North Carolina - Wilmington; Ali Watts, Bowling Green State University; Dajanae Palmer, University of Missouri*

Mapping the Questions: Supporting Qualitative Interview Analysis Through Emergent Structure. *Zachary Lim, Harvard University*

From Protocol to Practice: Methodological Reflections on Focus Group Research. *Megan Botello, University of Delaware; Elena Silla, University of Delaware; Maya Josiam, University of Delaware; Samuel Kenney, University of Delaware; Tamara Turski, University of Delaware; Srujana Acharya, University of Delaware; Christina Areizaga Barbieri, University of Delaware; Amanda Jansen, University of Delaware*

Chair: *Katherine Lewis, Dominican University of California*
Discussant: *Edith P. Middleton, Teachers College, Columbia University*

34.077-9. Giftedness, Creativity, and Talent Roundtable:

Creativity and Achievement (Table 9). SIG-Research on Giftedness, Creativity and Talent; Roundtable Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

The Creative Classroom: Group Structure, Self-Efficacy, and Conformity Effects. *Yun kyoung Kim, Seoul National University; Seon-Young Lee, Seoul National University*

Scientific Creativity Profiles among Taiwanese Junior High School Students. *Ju-hui Wei, National Sun Yat-sen University; Liang-Chen Su, National Sun Yat-sen University; Thomas J. Smith, Northern Illinois University; Chi-Hsi Wu, National Sun Yat-sen University; Pui Yi Mok, National Sun Yat-sen University; Hsueh-Hua Chuang, National Sun Yat-sen University*

The Complex Relationship between Creativity and Academic Achievement. *Beatrice Ruiz, Baylor University; Madelyn Chance, Baylor University; Todd Kettler, Baylor University; Nilay Gunel, Baylor University*

The Effectiveness of Systematic Creativity Interventions with Secondary School Students. *Fangfang Cai, Johns Hopkins University; Jae Won Claire Shin, Johns Hopkins University; Jonathan A. Plucker, Johns Hopkins University*

Does More Schooling Boost Creativity? Cross-National Causal Evidence from PISA 2022. *Deepak Sharma, Indian Institute of Management*

Chair: *Nancy B. Hertzog, University of Washington*

34.078. Scholars of Color Mentoring Roundtable (Table 1); Roundtable Session

34.078-1. Scholars of Color Mentoring Roundtable (Table 1). Committee on Scholars of Color in Education; Roundtable Session Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 403A; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Transitioning from doctoral student to assistant professor. *Farzana Tabitha Saleem Adjah, Stanford University; Kevin Lawrence Henry, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Mildred Boveda, Pennsylvania State University; Bianca Jontae Baldrige, Harvard University*

Enabling well-being and self-care for faculty of color. *Yolanda Sealey-Ruiz, Teachers College, Columbia University; Lindsay Pérez Huber, California State University - Long Beach; Latoya Haynes-Thoby, University of Connecticut*

Diverse career paths from the doctorate. *Honey Walrond, University of California - Berkeley; Kofi Lomotey, Western Carolina University; Linda C. Tillman, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; William A. Smith, University of Utah*

Chair: *Laura E. Hernandez, Learning Policy Institute*

Division and SIG Posters

34.079. AERA Poster Session Thursday 9:45am; Poster Session

34.079-1. Higher Education and Student Learning Outcomes.

Division C - Learning and Instruction; Poster Session Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 9:45-11:15am

Posters:

1. Agency Perception Through Interactions: How Students' Verification and Revision Behaviours Influence GenAI Tool Perception (Poster 1). *Yao Qu, Nanyang Technological University*
2. Designing Chatbots for Higher-Order Thinking: A Comparative Study of Multiple Persona vs Tutor Chatbots (Poster 2). *Chee Kit Looi, The Education University of Hong Kong; Ziyang CHE, Central China Normal University; Dan Sun, Hangzhou Normal University; Longkai WU, Central China Normal University*
3. Exploring Relationships Between Implementation Activities, Usage, and Student Learning Outcomes in an Online Math Program (Poster 3). *Chun-Wei Kevin Huang, WestEd; Natalie Brezack, WestEd; Mingyu Feng, WestEd; Linlin Li, WestEd*
4. Interventions for Effective Online Learning in Higher Education: A Systematic Literature Review (Poster 4). *Qiujiu LI, Nanyang Technological University - National Institute of Education; Jenny Lee, University of California - Irvine; Waverly Tseng, University of California - Irvine; Di Xu, University of California - Irvine*
5. Patterns of Perceptions and Experiences With ChatGPT Among Global Higher Education Students: A Data-Driven Approach (Poster 5). *Yuqing Zou, University of New Mexico - Gallup; Chunrui Zou, University of Pennsylvania*
6. Perception and Use of Active Learning Classroom: Are They Related? (Poster 6). *Yiren Kong, Stony Brook University - SUNY; Young Sik Seo, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Tina Abbate, Stony Brook University - SUNY*
7. Regulating Learning through ChatGPT: Reflections from International Graduate Students (Poster 7). *Stephen Kwame Ameko, Utah State University; Stephen Emmanuel Abu, University of Alabama; Oguns Clement Audu, Oklahoma State University; Irene Boahemaa Kyereh, Utah State University; Asmaa Yazidi Alaoui, Utah State University; Johnson Gbedze, Utah State University; Rebecca Y. Bayeck, Utah State University*
8. Structured vs. Varied: A Cross-National Study of ICT Environments and Scientific Literacy in Singapore and the U.S. (Poster 8). *Yi Wu, Pennsylvania State University*
9. Supporting Cultural Learning with SVVR: Effects of a Two-Tier Questioning Approach Across High- and Low-Performing Students (Poster 9). *Yuting Chen, The Chinese*

University of Hong Kong; Morris Siu-Yung Jong, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Miao Yue, Chinese University of Hong Kong

10. Ten Technological Affordances for Student Engagement in Video Conferencing: A Scoping Review and Analysis (Poster 10). *Mengqian Wu, McGill University; Junzhu Su, McGill University; Kristof Boucher-Charbonneau, X2O Media; Nikki Lobczowski, McGill University*
11. The Digital Double-Edged Sword: Digital Leisure's Impact on East Asian Youth's Creative Thinking (Poster 11). *Jiheng Wu, Beijing Normal University 北京师范大学; WenXi Wu, Shaanxi Normal University; Qian Zhao, Beijing Normal University*
12. The Nonlinear Impact of Students' ICT Use on Creative Thinking: Evidence from PISA 2022 (Poster 12). *Ziyuan Lin, Nanjing Normal University; Shanchun Wei, Nanjing Normal University; Jijun Yao, Nanjing Normal University; Haiyue Jin, Nanjing Normal University*
13. What Matters Most: A Mixed-Methods Study of Educational App Preferences Among Parents and Educators (Poster 13). *Hongrui Yuan, University of Michigan; Yuyue Zhao, University of Michigan; Thomas Michael Drake, University of Michigan; Elizabeth Keren-Kolb, University of Michigan; Heidi Bennett, University of Michigan*

34.079-2. Reimagining Inclusive Learning Environments.

Division C - Learning and Instruction; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 9:45-11:15am

Posters:

14. An Ecological Perspective on Sense of School Belonging Gap among Language Minority Students (Poster 14). *Yan Wu, Johns Hopkins University; Marcia H. Davis, Johns Hopkins University*
15. Bridging UDL and Andragogy in Graduate Education: Inclusive Strategies for Adult Learners (Poster 15). *Paul D. Miller, Montgomery College*
16. Cross-Age Peer Tutoring in Robotics: A Path to Computational Thinking (Poster 16). *Charoula M. Angeli, University of Cyprus; Vasia Anastasiou, University of Cyprus*
17. Developing the REAL-STEM (Research-Engaged Active Learning in STEM) Framework: Integrating Inquiry and Research for Transformative STEM Education (Poster 17). *Grace Jeonghyun Kim, University of Maryland; Sungwon Jung, University of Texas at Austin*
18. Envisioning Joyful Learning Futures: Inspiration from Caregiver Narratives (Poster 18). *Luna Laliberte, Stanford University; Brigid Barron, Stanford University; Sophie Chen, Stanford University; Caitlin Martin, Stanford University; Flora Troy*
19. Portraits of Excellence: Supporting Student Success in Introductory Statistics Courses (Poster 19). *Dalila Dragnic-Cindric, Digital Promise; Vanessa Peters Hinton, Digital*

Promise

20. Systematic Review of Interventions That Modify Physical Environments for Autistic Individuals (Poster 20). *IN SUK RYU, Korea University; Joonheon Kwon, Korea University; Dakyeom Lee, Korea University; Shannon LaPoint, Florida State University; So-Yeon Kim, Duksung Women's University; Hyunjo Ji, Seoul National University Hospital; Seunghyun Son, Korea University; So Yoon Kim, Korea University*

34.079-3. Division H Poster Session: Assessment in Schools.

Division H - Research, Evaluation and Assessment in Schools; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 9:45-11:15am

Posters:

21. Assessment model incorporating reflection to support the development of a self-directed learner in lower secondary education (Poster 21). *Annika Kuus, Rõuge Basic School; Katre Lambot, Tallinn French Lyceum; Kerli Kõiv, University of Tartu; Katrin Saks, University of Tartu*
22. From Feedback Reception to Achievement: The Critical Role of Feedback Orientation and Utilization in Education (Poster 22). *Lan Yang, Education University of Hong Kong; Lijie Qin, The Education University of Hong Kong; Kam Tai Tony Kwan, The Education University of Hong Kong*
23. Generative AI as a Credibility Scaffold in Peer Assessment: Evidence from a Chinese Undergraduate Course (Poster 23). *Lin Dai, East China Normal University; Jing Leng, East China Normal University; Honghuan Lu, East China Normal University*

34.079-4. Div J, Section 4 Poster Session 2. Division J -

Postsecondary Education; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 9:45-11:15am

Posters:

24. Rethinking the First-Year Seminar: Examining the Return on Investment by Instructor Role and Preparation (Poster 24). *Jamil D. Johnson, University of South Carolina; Masha Krsmanovic, University of Southern Mississippi; Kevin Wenger, University of South Carolina*
25. Roles of Change Agents in Discussion Network for Undergraduate Education: Insights from a Department Action Team Case (Poster 25). *Jaeyun Han, University of Illinois at Chicago; Fructoso M Basaldua, University of Illinois at Chicago; Mikayla Strasser, University of Illinois at Chicago; Susan P Farruggia, University of Illinois at Chicago; Carmen Lilley, University of Illinois at Chicago; Mike Stieff, University of Illinois at Chicago*
26. Video-Based Collaborative Microteaching for Faculty PD: Design Features, Reflective Impact, and Pedagogical Implications (Poster 26). *Gyeong Mi Heo, Korea University; Boyoung Kim, Korea University*

34.079-5. Reimagining Children's Creativity Through Narrative Inquiry and Listening Pedagogy. SIG-Action Research; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 9:45-11:15am

Poster:

27. Reimagining Children's Creativity Through Narrative Inquiry and Listening Pedagogy (Poster 27). *Hyejin Do, San Francisco State University; Mina Kim, San Francisco State University*

34.079-6. AERA Division K Section 6 In-Service Educators - Poster Session 2. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 9:45-11:15am

Posters:

28. Beyond tokenism: Reflection as an opportunity for imagining pedagogical futures in teacher development (Poster 28). *Carmel Geneva Roofe, University of the West Indies - Mona Campus*
29. Building Teacher Capacity for Culturally Responsive Computing in Indigenous-Serving Schools (Poster 29). *Wei Yan, Northern Arizona University; Priyanka Parekh, Northern Arizona University; Ashish Amresh, Northern Arizona University; Paige Prescott, Computer Science Alliance; Arden Day, Northern Arizona University; Jeffrey Hovermill, Northern Arizona University*
30. Coaching, Collaboration, and Futuring: A Biopsychosocial Praxis (Poster 30). *Eva I. Diaz, University of Arkansas at Fayetteville; Socorro Herrera, Kansas State University; Diana Gonzales Worthen, University of Arkansas at Fayetteville*
31. Do Teachers' Professional Development Efforts Pay Off? A Meta-Analysis of Effects on Student Achievement (Poster 31). *John Darag, University of Northern Colorado; Sue Hyeon Paek, University of Northern Colorado*
32. From Classrooms to State Policy: Factors Shaping Teacher Collaboration and Expertise Sharing (Poster 32). *Robin Keturah Anderson, North Carolina State University; Temple A. Walkowiak, North Carolina State University; Shaun B. Kellogg, North Carolina State University*
33. How Secondary Teachers Adapt Instruction in Response to Classroom Linguistic Diversity (Poster 33). *Eunjee Jang, University of Wisconsin - River Falls; Kyung Sun Chung, Columbia College Chicago; Bong Gee Jang, Syracuse University*
34. Inquiry Against Silence: Teaching the Tulsa Race Massacre Despite Legislative Barriers (Poster 34). *Shanetra Dilese Nowell, Oklahoma State University; Shelbie Witte, University of North Dakota*
35. Intentional Collaboration to Challenge Researcher-Teacher Power Dynamics and Promote Productive Mutual Exchanges

(Poster 35). *Martha Inouye, University of Wyoming; Clare Gunshenan, University of Wyoming*

36. Online Informal Learning and Calling as Predictors of Teacher Engagement: The Role of Self-Efficacy (Poster 36). *Shiyu Zhang, University of Hong Kong; Xianhan Huang, The Education University of Hong Kong; Wen SHAO, University of Hong Kong; Chan Wang, The Education University of Hong Kong; Mingyao Sun, Hong Kong Polytechnic University*
37. Planning to Plan with Teachers: Coaches' Aims for Supporting Teachers' Learning in Co-planning Conversations (Poster 37). *Nicholas M. Kochmanski, University of North Carolina - Greensboro; Sevim Sevgi, Erciyes University*
38. Sustaining Pedagogical Change: Educator Practice in the Year Following the LaCuKnoS DBIR Project (Poster 38). *Melissa Livingston, Oregon State University; Cory A. Buxton, Oregon State University; Camila Cigarroa Kennedy, Education Northwest*
39. Teachers' Development of Computational Thinking (CT) Skills and TPACK from Three Visual Programming Platforms (Poster 39). *Youjung Jung, Northern Illinois University; Ying Xie, Northern Illinois University*
40. Transforming Curriculum Leadership Through School-Based Professional Development in Japan (Poster 40). *Tetsuo Kuramoto, Shizuoka University Art and Culture; Kenji Tsuyuguchi, Ehime University*
41. Voices from the Classroom: Contextualizing Social Emotional Learning in Kenya Through Educator Perspectives (Poster 41). *Shinchieh Duh, San Jose State University; Igor Himelfarb, National Board of Chiropractic Examiners; JACINTA AKATSA, CEMASTE; Jong Tak Lee, Grow X Education; Rita Rodriguez, San Francisco State University; Jae H. Paik, San Francisco State University*
42. Weaving Relational Approaches in World Language Teacher Learning: Embodiment, Creative Expression and Connection (Poster 42). *Seyyedeh Mobina Hosseini, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Erin Kearney, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

34.080. Meet the Editors - Journal Talks Session 2. AERA Sessions; Journal Talks

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

1. AERA Open (Table 1). *Gustavo E. Fischman, Arizona State University; Audrey Amrein-Beardsley, Arizona State University; Natasha Sterzinger, AERA Open; Angela M. Labistre Champion, Pennsylvania State University*
2. American Journal of Education (Table 2). *Emily M. Hodge, Virginia Commonwealth University; Dana L. Mitra, Pennsylvania State University; Daniel Robotham, Penn State*
3. Arts Education Policy Review (Table 3). *Kenneth Elpus, University of Maryland*

4. Assessment in Education: Principles, Policy & Practice (Table 4). *Christopher DeLuca, Queen's University - Kingston*
5. Berkeley Review of Education (Table 5). *Aukeem A. Ballard, University of California - Berkeley; Ilke Bayazitli, University of California - Berkeley; Emely Natali Lugo, University of California - Berkeley*
6. California Journal of Politics and Policy (Table 6). *Amal Kumar, California State University - Sacramento*
7. ECNU Review of Education (Table 7). *Yi Jiang, East China Normal University; Jiani Rong, East China Normal University; chenlu liu, East China Normal University*
8. Educational Media International (Table 8). *Sandra Schamroth Abrams, University of South Africa*
9. Educational Philosophy and Theory (Table 9). *Liz Jackson, University of Hong Kong; Marek Tesar, University of Melbourne*
10. Educational Psychologist (Table 10). *Jason A. Chen, College of William & Mary; Krista R. Muis, McGill University*
11. Educational Studies (Table 11). *Ming Fang He, Georgia Southern University; Bic Ngo, University of Minnesota; Suniti Sharma, Saint Joseph's University; Boni Wozolek, Pennsylvania State University - Abington*
12. English Teaching: Practice & Critique (Table 12). *Audrey Lucero, University of Oregon; Amy Vetter, University of North Carolina - Greensboro; Melissa Schieble, Hunter College - CUNY*
13. Equity & Excellence in Education (Table 13). *Kysa Nygreen, University of Massachusetts - Amherst; Denise Ives, University of Massachusetts - Amherst*
14. International Journal of Designs for Learning (IJDL) (Table 14). *Ahmed Lachheb, University of Kansas; Victoria Abramenka-Lachheb, University of Michigan; Elizabeth Boling, Indiana University; Justin Sentz, Old Dominion University; Sonia Tiwari, Kids AI; Colin M. Gray, Indiana University; Karen Smith, Indiana University*
15. Educational Researcher (Table 15). *Angela Urick, Baylor University*
16. Journal of Early Childhood Literacy (Table 16). *Deborah Rowe, Vanderbilt University; Lisa K Kervin, University of Wollongong; Fiona Scott, University of Sheffield*
17. Improving Schools (Table 17). *Sedat Gümüş, The Education University of Hong Kong; Martin Brown, Dublin City University; Shelley Zion, Rowan University*
18. Change: The Magazine of Higher Learning (Table 18). *KC Culver, University of Alabama*
19. Journal of College and Character (Table 19). *Laura Harrison, Ohio University*
20. Gifted Child Today (Table 20). *Fred A. Bonner, Prairie View A&M University*

34.081. e-Lightning Ed-Talk Session 7 - Stage 1. AERA e-Lightning Ed-Talks; AERA Ed Talk

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Exhibit Hall A - Stage 1; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- Developing the REAL-STEM (Research-Engaged Active Learning in STEM) Framework: Integrating Inquiry and Research for Transformative STEM Education (Stage 1, 9:50 AM). *Grace Jeonghyun Kim, University of Maryland; Sungwon Jung, University of Texas at Austin*
- Systematic Review of Interventions That Modify Physical Environments for Autistic Individuals (Stage 1, 9:59 AM). *IN SUK RYU, Korea University; Joonheon Kwon, Korea University; Dakyeom Lee, Korea University; Shannon LaPoint, Florida State University; So-Yeon Kim, Duksung Women's University; Hyunjo Ji, Seoul National University Hospital; Seunghyun Son, Korea University; So Yoon Kim, Korea University*
- Designing Chatbots for Higher-Order Thinking: A Comparative Study of Multiple Persona vs Tutor Chatbots (Stage 1, 10:08 AM). *Chee Kit Looi, The Education University of Hong Kong; Ziyang CHE, Central China Normal University; Dan Sun, Hangzhou Normal University; Longkai WU, Central China Normal University*
- Regulating Learning through ChatGPT: Reflections from International Graduate Students (Stage 1, 10:17 AM). *Stephen Kwame Ameko, Utah State University; Stephen Emmanuel Abu, University of Alabama; Oguns Clement Adu, Oklahoma State University; Irene Boahemaa Kyereh, Utah State University; Asmaa Yazidi Alaoui, Utah State University; Johnson Gbedze, Utah State University; Rebecca Y. Bayeck, Utah State University*
- Structured vs. Varied: A Cross-National Study of ICT Environments and Scientific Literacy in Singapore and the U.S. (Stage 1, 10:26 AM). *Yi Wu, Pennsylvania State University*
- The Role of Complex Learning Interactions and Cognitive Load in Immersive Virtual Reality-based Chemistry Simulations (Stage 1, 10:35 AM). *Maral Karimi, University of Central Florida; Megan Wiedbusch, University of Central Florida; Cameron Marano, University of Central Florida; Annamarie Broshinan, University of Central Florida; Tara Brianna Delgado, University of Central Florida; Marta Sobocinski, University of Oulu; Natalie Blaize, University of Central Florida; Romina Jannotti, Trinity Preparatory School; Roger Azevedo, University of Central Florida*
- Roles of Change Agents in Discussion Network for Undergraduate Education: Insights from a Department Action Team Case (Stage 1, 10:44 AM). *Jaeyun Han, University of Illinois at Chicago; Fructoso M Basaldua, University of Illinois at Chicago; Mikayla Strasser, University of Illinois at Chicago; Susan P Farruggia, University of Illinois at Chicago; Carmen Lilley, University of Illinois at Chicago; Mike Stieff, University of Illinois at Chicago*

Chair: *Xiaoxia A. Newton, University of North Carolina - Charlotte*

34.082. e-Lightning Ed-Talk Session 7 - Stage 2. AERA e-Lightning Ed-Talks; AERA Ed Talk
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Exhibit Hall A
- Stage 2; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Beyond tokenism: Reflection as an opportunity for imagining pedagogical futures in teacher development (Stage 2, 9:50 AM). *Carmel Geneva Roofe, University of the West Indies - Mona Campus*

Building Teacher Capacity for Culturally Responsive Computing in Indigenous-Serving Schools (Stage 2, 9:59 AM). *Wei Yan, Northern Arizona University; Priyanka Parekh, Northern Arizona University; Ashish Amresh, Northern Arizona University; Paige Prescott, Computer Science Alliance; Arden Day, Northern Arizona University; Jeffrey Hovermill, Northern Arizona University*

Coaching, Collaboration, and Futuring: A Biopsychosocial Praxis (Stage 2, 10:08 AM). *Eva I. Diaz, University of Arkansas at Fayetteville; Socorro Herrera, Kansas State University; Diana Gonzales Worthen, University of Arkansas at Fayetteville*

Inquiry Against Silence: Teaching the Tulsa Race Massacre Despite Legislative Barriers (Stage 2, 10:17 AM). *Shanetra Dilese Nowell, Oklahoma State University; Shelby Witte, University of North Dakota*

Sustaining Pedagogical Change: Educator Practice in the Year Following the LaCuKnoS DBIR Project (Stage 2, 10:26 AM). *Melissa Livingston, Oregon State University; Cory A. Buxton, Oregon State University; Camila Cigarroa Kennedy, Education Northwest*

Voices from the Classroom: Contextualizing Social Emotional Learning in Kenya Through Educator Perspectives (Stage 2, 10:35 AM). *Shinchieh Duh, San Jose State University; Igor Himelfarb, National Board of Chiropractic Examiners; JACINTA AKATSA, CEMASTEIA; Jong Tak Lee, Grow X Education; Rita Rodriguez, San Francisco State University; Jae H. Paik, San Francisco State University*

Reimagining Children's Creativity Through Narrative Inquiry and Listening Pedagogy (Stage 2, 10:44 AM). *Hyejin Do, San Francisco State University; Mina Kim, San Francisco State University*

Chair: *Xiaoxia A. Newton, University of North Carolina - Charlotte*

Thursday, April 9th, 11:45 am

AERA Sessions

35.010. 2026 AERA Awards Ceremony and Luncheon. AERA Sessions; Invited Speaker Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Concourse

Hall; 11:45am to 1:45pm

Participants:

2026 Outstanding Book Award. *Gabrielle Oliveira, Harvard University; Ebony O. McGee, Johns Hopkins University*

2026 Review of Research Award. *Rebecca A. Cruz, Johns Hopkins University; Catherine Kramarczuk Voulgarides, Hunter College - CUNY; Allison Firestone, San Francisco Unified School District; Logan McDermott, Oregon State University; Zihui Feng, Johns Hopkins University; Antonio L. Ellis, American University*

2026 Palmer O. Johnson Memorial Award. *Sean Darling-Hammond, University of California - Berkeley; Eric Ho, McGraw-Hill; Catherine P. Bradshaw, University of Virginia*

2026 Scholars of Color in Education Early Career Contribution Award. *Terrell R Morton, University of Illinois at Chicago; Laura E. Hernandez, Learning Policy Institute*

2026 Scholars of Color in Education Mid-Career Contribution Award. *Cezare A. Warren, Vanderbilt University; Laura E. Hernandez, Learning Policy Institute*

2026 Scholars of Color in Education Distinguished Career Contribution Award. *William Perez, Loyola Marymount University; Laura E. Hernandez, Learning Policy Institute*

2026 Distinguished Contributions to Gender Equity in Education Research Award. *Lara Perez-Felkner, Florida State University; Francesca López, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

2026 Exemplary Contributions to Practice-Engaged Research Award. *Nicole Patton-Terry, Florida State University; Sarah L. Woulfin, University of Texas at Austin*

2026 Social Justice in Education Award. *Angela Valenzuela, University of Texas at Austin; Denise M. Taliaferro Baszile, Wayne State University*

2026 E. F. Lindquist Award. *Michael J. Kolen, University of Iowa; Mary Pitoniak, Pitoniak Educational Measurement*

2026 Outstanding Public Communication of Education Research Award. *Nolan L. Cabrera, University of Arizona; Guofang Li, University of British Columbia*

2026 Excellence in Media Reporting on Education Research Award. *Sarah Carr, Columbia University; Lalitha Vasudevan, Teachers College, Columbia University*

2026 Dr. Felice J. Levine Distinguished Contributions to Mentoring in Research and Leadership Award. *Vivian L. Gadsden, University of Pennsylvania; Janelle T. Scott, University of California - Berkeley*

2026 Early Career Award. *Cati V. de los Rios, University of California - Berkeley; Alfredo J. Artiles, Stanford University*

2026 Distinguished Public Service Award. *James L. Moore, National Science Foundation; Elizabeth H. DeBray, University of Georgia*

2026 Distinguished Contributions to Research in Education Award. *Vivian L. Gadsden, University of Pennsylvania; Shaun R. Harper, University of Southern California*

Chairs: *Tabbye M. Chavous, American Educational Research Association; Maisha T. Winn, Stanford University*

Thursday, April 9th, 12:00 pm

SIG Sessions

36.010. Off-Site Visit to Tour CANDLE(Center for Affective Neuroscience, Development, Learning and Education) at USC. SIG-Brain, Neurosciences and Education Cosponsored with SIG-Classroom Management, SIG-Montessori Education; Off-Site Visit
University of Southern California, CANDLE(Center for Affective Neuroscience, Development, Learning and Education) at USC; 12:00-3:30pm
Visit Leaders: *Kay Brocato, Mississippi State University; Mary Helen Immordino-Yang, University of Southern California*

Thursday, April 9th, 2:00 pm

37.010. zzzzz Cancelled per Email 3-2-26 Equity & Excellence in Education Journal Editorial Board Meeting. Affiliated Groups; Board Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Level 3, Santa Monica D; 2:00-4:00pm

Thursday, April 9th, 2:15 pm

Governance Meetings and Events

38.001. AERA Equity and Inclusion Council: Closed Meeting. AERA Governance; Governance Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 513; 2:15-3:45pm
Chair: *Terrell R Morton, University of Illinois at Chicago*

38.002. AERA Open: Closed Editorial Board Meeting. AERA Governance; Governance Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 518; 2:15-3:45pm
Chair: *John Neikirk, American Educational Research Association*

Presidential Sessions

38.010. AERA Tiny Desk Scholarly Discographies. AERA Presidential Session; Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 408A; 2:15-3:45pm

Chair: *Shaun R. Harper, University of Southern California*
Speakers: *Rema E. Reynolds Vassar, Wayne State University; Lori Patton Davis, University of California, Los Angeles; Christopher Emdin, Teachers College, Columbia University; Gloria J. Ladson-Billings, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Yolanda Sealey-Ruiz, Teachers College, Columbia University; Gholdy Muhammad, University of Chicago*

38.011. The Future of AI in Education: Research, Policy, and Public Impact. AERA Presidential Session; Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 406AB; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Spark Talk Team 1. *Victor R. Lee, Stanford University; Ibrahim Oluwajoba Adisa, Stanford University*

Spark Team 2. *Safiya Noble, University of California - Los Angeles; Tiera C. Tanksley, University of Colorado - Boulder*

Spark Team 3. *Prudence L. Carter, Brown University; Malik Boykin, Brown University*

Spark Team 4. *Allison Scott, Kapor Center for Social Impact*
Spark Team 5. *James L. Moore, National Science Foundation; Angela Haydel DeBarger, William and Flora Hewlett Foundation*

Chairs: *Na'ilah Suad Nasir, Spencer Foundation; Sepehr Vakil, Northwestern University*

Discussant: *Ezekiel J. Dixon-Roman, Teachers College, Columbia University*

38.012. Wake & Whirlwinds: (Re)Constructing Global Black Southern Girlhood Stories Amidst Climate Change and Implications for Educational Research. AERA Presidential Session; Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 404AB; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Surge and Currents: Navigating the Outer Bands. *Tiffany O. Harris, College of Charleston; Taryn T.C. Brown, University of Florida; Bria Harper, Wofford College*

In the Eye(s) of the Storm: Documenting the Groundwork. *Kiana González Cedeño, Texas Christian University; Lauren Prince, Brown University; Lauren Elizabeth Reine Johnson, University of Illinois at Chicago*

Chair: *Tamara Butler, College of Charleston*

Discussant: *April D. Baker-Bell, University of Michigan*

AERA Research and Science Policy Sessions

38.013. The Elementary and Secondary Education Act at 60: Looking Back and Future Prospect. AERA Science and

Policy Sessions; Invited Speaker Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 408B;
2:15-3:45pm

Chair: *Elizabeth H. DeBray, University of Georgia*
Participants: *Geoffrey D. Borman, Arizona State University;*
Sheneka M. Williams, Michigan State University; Kara S.
Finnigan, University of Michigan; Walker A. Swain, LPI

AERA Sessions

38.014. Emotion, Identity, and Social Contexts in Learning.

Division C - Learning and Instruction Cosponsored with
SIG-Motivation in Education; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall -
Exhibit Hall A; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

1. Creative Attitudes and Values as a Buffer Against the Pitfalls of AI Self-Efficacy (Poster 1). *Xiaofei Lyu, Tsinghua University; Chanchan Liu, Tsinghua University; Jun Wei, Tsinghua University*
2. Elementary Teachers' Emotional Landscape: Insights Beyond Existing Literature (Poster 2). *Dionne Cross Francis, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Boran Yu, University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill; Yijia Chen, University of Arizona; Lijie Liu, University of Arizona; Ji Y. Hong, University of Arizona*
3. Gender differences in the influences of social support on student motivation and proficiency in EFL (Poster 3). *Wenjuan Guo, Shanghai Jiao Tong University; Yuxi Zhang, Shanghai Jiao Tong University*
4. Independent and Interdependent Self-Construals as Predictors of Group Work Engagement and Perceived Effectiveness in STEM (Poster 4). *Katie Jacobson, University of Oregon; Aleya Dhanji, Highline Community College; Eric Baer, Highline Community College; Matthew C. Graham, University of Oregon*
5. Keeping Up with the Classmates: Building a Nomological Network of Student Envy (Poster 5). *Flora Fassl, University of Vienna; Dayeon Jeong, Korea University - Brain and Motivation Research Institute; Maximilian Hofleitner, University of Vienna; Mimi Bong, Korea University; Marko Lüftenecker, Universität Wien*
6. Profiling English Learners' Negative Emotions: Motivational Antecedents, Emotion Regulation, and Achievement across Genders (Poster 6). *Yuhong Jiao, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Barry Bai, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Hongfang Li, Baicaooyuan Kindergarten; Qingyao Dan, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Jiatong Zhang, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; To Chan, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Miranda Lin, Illinois State University*
7. Seeing the Source, Trusting the Source: What Helps Children Navigate Conflicting Texts? (Poster 7). *Haolan Wang,*

Beijing Normal University; Xinchun Wu, Beijing Normal University

8. An Exploratory Study of Interest-Boredom Detection Using Facial Action Units during Interactive Reading (Poster 8). *Qiyuan Zheng, University of Toronto - OISE; Jiaju Huang, University of Toronto - OISE; Earl Woodruff, University of Toronto - OISE; Suzanne E. Hidi, University of Toronto*
9. Are Punnett Squares Just a Science-Specific Spatial Reasoning Task? Middle School Students See it Differently (Poster 9). *Jazelle Pilato, University of Pittsburgh; Emily Grossnickle Peterson, American University*
10. Beyond Up and Down: Competitiveness as a Moderator of Multidirectional Social Comparisons in Adolescent Learning (Poster 10). *Yuejia Gao, East China Normal University; Yi Jiang, East China Normal University*
11. How Seductive Details Affect EFL Learners' Comprehension of English Science Texts (Poster 11). *Gan Jin, Washington State University; Yingru Zhao, University at Albany - SUNY; Yu Xue, Washington State University; Dongni Guo, University at Albany - SUNY; Shiyan Yang, Dalian University of Foreign Languages; Yafeng Liu, Dalian University of Foreign Languages; Robert W. Danielson, Washington State University - Spokane*
12. Learning Psychological Capital and Extracurricular Tutoring : Heterogeneous Effects on Middle Students' Academics (Poster 12). *nengjun Zhao, Nanjing Normal University 南京师范大学; Jijun Yao, Nanjing Normal University*
13. The Moderating Effects of Prior Vocabulary on Growth in Comprehension and Metacognitive Monitoring (Poster 13). *Willow Alston-Socha, North Carolina State University; John L. Nietfeld, North Carolina State University*
14. To lead and succeed: How leadership and global satisfaction relates to achievement of secondary students (Poster 14). *Yaolan Weng, The Ohio State University; Brenda Rojas Amarilla, The Ohio State University; Andrew Holmes Perry, The Ohio State University; Eric M. Anderman, The Ohio State University; Rich Gilman, Terrace Metrics, Inc*
15. Beyond the Surface: Unpacking Hidden Conflicts in Student Motivation through the Iceberg Model (Poster 15). *Harish Premi, Indian Institute of Management*

38.014. Division G VP Session: The Social Context of Education and MSI's.

Division G - Social Context of
Education; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall -
Exhibit Hall A; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

16. Unpacking the Performativity of Hispanic Serving Institution (HSI) Designation: Holding the University of Accountable and Developing a Call to Action (Poster 16). *Nancy López, University of New Mexico; Angeles Rubi Castorena, University of California - Irvine; Florence Emily*

Castillo, Texas Christian University

17. Asian American Pacific Islander-Serving Institution (AANAPISI) Do Build Social Capital: Strategies Supporting the Success of Southeast Asian American Students (Poster 17). *Phitsamay Sychitkokhong Uy, University of Massachusetts - Lowell*
18. Hispanic-Serving Institutions as Crucial Sites to Promote, Transform, and Re-Imagine STEM Education for Intersectional Justice (Poster 18). *Luis Antonio Leyva, Vanderbilt University*
19. Black Undergraduates' Sense-Making of Identity, "Success," and The Promise of Higher Education (Poster 19). *Sagen Kidane, Brown University*
20. Beyond Survival: Recognizing Student Courage, Increasing Resilience, and Overcoming the Odds (Poster 20). *Kathy Hayes, LAUSD*
21. Navigating a successful pathway through academia for early career scholars (Poster 21). *Jodi Burshia, New Mexico Highlands University (NMHU)*
22. More Than Money: Hispanic-Serving Institutions (HSIs) and the Multiple Dimensions of Social Mobility (Poster 22). *Marcela G. Cuellar, University of California - Davis; Isabella D.C. Herrera, University of California - Davis*
23. A University and After School Community-Based MSI Program Collaboration in Detroit: On-going Strategies to Promote the College Access Pipeline (Poster 23). *K. Dara Hill, University of Michigan - Dearborn*
24. Cultural Attentiveness in Action: How Minority-Serving Institutions Prepare Justice-Centered Educators (Poster 24). *Romonda Middlebrooks-Jefferson, Georgia State University*

38.014. Bourdieu and Transnational Habitus. SIG-Bourdieu in Educational Research; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 2:15-3:45pm

Participant:

25. Exploring Transnational Habitus As A Framework To Understand International Student Mobilities: A Theoretical Approach (Poster 25). *Yifan Liu, University of Toronto*

38.014. Assessing and Supporting Self-Regulated Learning Across Learning Contexts. SIG-Studying and Self-Regulated Learning; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

26. Measuring Learner Autonomy in K-12: A Systematic Review of Assessment Instruments (Poster 26). *Xue Wang, Johns Hopkins University; Yinran Hao, Institute of Materia Medica, CAMS & PUMC; Zixuan Huang, Johns Hopkins University; Hanhui Bao, University of Tennessee; Marcia H. Davis, Johns Hopkins University*
27. Mechanisms of Adaptivity in ALTs to Foster SRL in K-12 Education: A Systematic Literature Review (Poster 27).

Ismail Souiri, University of Bern; Mathias Mejez, Fachhochschule Nordwestschweiz

28. Moderating Impact of Gender on Personality and Self-Regulated Learning with ChatGPT (Poster 28). *Yuk Mui Elly Heung, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Xiaojing Weng, The Education University of Hong Kong; Thomas K.F. Chiu, The Chinese University of Hong Kong*
29. Prior Knowledge, Confidence, and Their Effects on STEM Performance and Self-Regulated Learning Patterns (Poster 29). *Juan Zheng, Lehigh University; Shiyi Liu, Lehigh University; Shan Li, Lehigh University; Charles Xie, Institute for Future Intelligence*
30. Understanding the Effects of Simple Analogies on Comprehension and Metacomprehension in Geoscience (Poster 30). *Allison J. Jaeger, Mississippi State University; Micahel Poe, Mississippi State University; Thomas Daniel Griffin, University of Illinois at Chicago; Jennifer Wiley, University of Illinois at Chicago; Lena Hildenbrand, University of Illinois at Chicago; Nicole D LaDue, Northern Illinois University*
31. Unpacking Goal Setting in Digital Learning: Mediators and Moderators Informing New Educational Designs (Poster 31). *Anait Akopyan, University of Tartu*
32. Validating 'E' in STEM: How Engineering Fosters Self-Regulation and 21C Skills in Korean High Schools (Poster 32). *Woongbin Park, Purdue University; Hyeree Cho, Purdue University; Huiy Lim, Seoul metropolitan office of education; Yunjin Lim, Chinju National University of Education; Hyumuk Park, Purdue University; Jiwon Kim, Purdue University*

38.014. Creative Pedagogies: Storytelling, Joy, and Radical Imagination in Black Education. SIG-Research Focus on Black Education; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

33. Resilience Strategies among Black Male Students in the U.S. Education System. A systematic review (Poster 33). *Malachi Okechi Chukwu, Washington State University; Olusola Olalekan Adesope, Washington State University*
34. Solange, Storytelling, and Sankofa: A Conversation on Black Women's Joy and Intellectual Traditions (Poster 34). *Linnsey McFerguson, Florida Atlantic University*
35. Supporting Black Students in California Community Colleges During The Era Of AB 705 Legislative Reform (Poster 35). *Julia Camille Ransom, Research for Action; Kri Burkander, Research for Action; Taylor Stenley, Research for Action; Dae Y. Kim, Research for Action*
36. Black Urban Storytelling and Thuglife Philosophy: A Radical Framework for Reclaiming Black Male Identity and Success in Educational Spaces (Poster 36). *Shanice Nicole Robinson, San Francisco State University*

38.014. Research Engagement and Development with Youth (READY) Program Invited Poster Session. AERA

Sessions; Invited Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

37. Data Breachers: Youth Counterstories in Quantitative Education Research (Poster 37). *Wendy Castillo, Montclair State University; Juan Andrés Ouviaña, Montclair State University; Marielyn Hidalgo, Montclair State University; Jeidyamar Molina-Cruz, Newark School of Data Science & Information Technology; Aolani Perez, Newark School of Data Science & Information Technology; Oluwadamilare Ashaolu, Newark School of Data Science & Information Technology; Mishael Adesoji, Newark School of Data Science & Information Technology; Daniel Asebiomo, Newark Public Schools*
38. Ethnic Studies and the Praxis of Transgressive-Racialization: Liberation Learners Exploring the Unmaking of Race (Poster 38). *Jonathan Desmon Russell Pérez, The School of The New York Times; Kimberly Jimenez-Martin, Coliseum College Prep Academy; Jesus Gutierrez Flores, Coliseum College Prep Academy; Juan Chavez Martinez, Coliseum College Prep Academy; Icker Merida Gramajo, Coliseum College Prep Academy; Christian Hernandez Martinez, Coliseum College Prep Academy; Tajanea Clark, Coliseum College Prep Academy*
39. Lexington Student Research and Publication Collaborative (Poster 39). *Alexa Muse, University of Oxford; Aanya Kaveti, Lexington High School; Angela Xie, Lexington High School; Amal Balachundhar, Lexington High School; Rocio Salgado Rodriguez, Lexington High School; Cameron Mantha, Lexington High School; Noe Voskuil, Lexington High School*
40. Robotico: Students Empowering Diverse Future Talents in STEM (Poster 40). *Insook Han, Korea University; Stella Kwon, Korea International School; Justin An, Korea International School; Ian Shin, Korea International School*
41. UCLA Community Schools: Civic Engagement Scholar Youth Team (Poster 41). *Jeffrey Yo, University of California - Los Angeles; Karen Hunter Quartz, University of California - Los Angeles; Valerie Manzo Munguia, Mann UCLA Community School; Abraham May, Mann UCLA Community School; Warenn Trujeque, Mann UCLA Community School; Maria Jillian Santos, UCLA Community School; Iolani Brideau, UCLA Community School*
42. Who Will Teach Us Next? Ohio High School Students' Perceptions of Teaching as a Career (Poster 42). *Adam Voight, Cleveland State University; Cora Barcelona, Lakewood High School; Maya Trempe, Lakewood High School; Breanna Kern, Richmond Heights High School; Ryan Hilcu, Brooklyn High School; Abigail Peck, Lakewood High School*

Chair: *Lori Diane Hill, American Educational Research Association*

Committee Sessions

38.015. Division E Fireside Chat: Navigating the PhD and Unpacking the Hidden Curriculum.

Graduate Student Council Cosponsored with Division E - Counseling and Human Development; Invited Speaker Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 402A; 2:15-3:45pm

Chairs: *Yi-Yun Tsai, College of William & Mary; Gabriella M. Soqui, University of California - Los Angeles*

Panelists: *Latoya Haynes-Thoby, University of Connecticut; Cebrail Karayigit, Rowan University; Anna J. Markowitz, University of California - Los Angeles; Yan Jiang, Stanford University; Robert Richard Martinez, William & Mary*

38.016. Language, Culture, and Citizenship: Global Education for Diverse Communities.

International Relations Committee; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 502A; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Conscious Storytelling: Global Changemakers Navigating Growth, Guiding Learning, and Honoring Culture Using Translanguaging and Expression. *Rebekka J. Jez, University of San Diego*

Examining the Link Between Immigrant Families' Early Care and Education Attendance and Public Assistance Program Participation. *Ekaterina Novikova, University of Delaware; Rena Hallam, University of Delaware*

Exploring the Impact of Global Citizenship Education on European Youth: A Cross-National Perspective. *Maria Teresa Tatto, Arizona State University; Andres Sandoval-Hernandez, University of Bath; Zhijun Chen, University of Bath*

Governing Language, Access, Knowledge: Comparative Language Policy in the United Nations, European Union, and African Union. *Honorine Ntoh Yuh, University of Alabama*

Chair: *Ozge Yalciner, University of Kentucky*

Discussant: *Lina Safa, Pepperdine University*

38.017. Leadership and Gender Equity: Lessons Learned that Cannot be Forgotten.

Committee on Scholars and Advocates for Gender Equity in Education; Invited Speaker Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 303A; 2:15-3:45pm

Chair: *Margaret-Mary Sulentic Dowell, Louisiana State University*
Discussant: *Kevin Lawrence Henry, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Panelists: *Estela Zarate, Loyola Marymount University; Henderson Lewis, Louisiana State University*

International Organization Sessions

38.018. Leadership, Innovation and Collaboration: New Imaginings for School Effectiveness and Improvement. International Aligned Organizations/International Congress for School Effectiveness and School Improvement - ICSEI; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum B; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Catalysts of Change: School Leadership and Innovation in Education. *Nicola Sum, Monash University; Stephen W. MacGregor, University of Calgary; Paul Campbell, The University of Hong Kong*

Sustaining Productive Teacher Collaborations: Insights across International Contexts. *Bryant Jensen, Brigham Young University; Paul Campbell, The University of Hong Kong*

Enhancing collaboration between school professionals and local communities. *Sara Romiti, INVALSI; Anton Florek, The Staff College; Mohammed Elmeski, Sigma Associates Incorporated Minnesota*

Chair: *Danette Parsley, Marzano Research*

Discussant: *James P. Spillane, Northwestern University*

Division Sessions

38.019. Conceptual and Empirical Examination of Educational Leadership Development. Division A - Administration; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, La Brea; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Interconnection as Developmental Capacity: Growing Toward Collective Leadership for Justice. *Eleanor E. Drago-Severson, Teachers College, Columbia University; Jessica Blum-DeStefano, Bank Street College of Education; Deborah Brooks Lawrence, Bank Street College of Education*

Lost in Terminology Jungle: Uncovering Jingle-Jangle Fallacies in Educational Leadership Research Literature. *Yinying Wang, Georgia State University*

Hiring School Leaders: Exploring the School Principal Selection Process in an Urban District. *Michelle Doughty, Vanderbilt University; Jason A. Grissom, Vanderbilt University*

Can Standardized HR Processes Enhance Leadership Diversity in Schools? A District Case Study. *Henry Tran, University of South Carolina; David G. Buckman, University of South Carolina - Aiken; Suzy Hardie, University of South Carolina; Simone A. F. Gause, Coastal Carolina University; David G. Martinez, University of South Carolina*

Chair: *Jerry Ray Burkett, University of North Texas at Dallas*

Discussant: *Doron Zinger, California State University - Dominguez Hills*

38.020. AI-Mediated Learning Environments: Scaffolding Inquiry, Metacognition, and Engagement. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Palos Verdes; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Evaluating Instructional Alignment in LLM-Generated Math Tasks Using Expert Teacher Annotations. *Patrick Oluyori Akinwumi, Clemson University; Meihua Qian, Clemson University*

Impact of a GenAI-assisted Socratic Dialogue Tool on Learning in an Asynchronous Computer Science Course. *Jeonghyun Lee, Georgia Institute of Technology; Meryem Yilmaz Soyulu, Georgia Institute of Technology; Jui-Tse Hung, Georgia Institute of Technology; Diana Popescu, Georgia Institute of Technology; Christopher Cui, University of California - San Diego; Gayane Grigoryan, Georgia Institute of Technology; David Joyner, Georgia Institute of Technology; Stephen W Harmon, Georgia Institute of Technology*

Parental Perceptions of Value in a Social Media Space for Early Childhood Family STEM Learning. *Valentina Bongiovanni, University of North Florida; Meghan M. Parkinson, University of North Florida; Daniel Dinsmore, University of North Florida*

The AI as Cognitive Mentor: Scaffolding Student Scientific Inquiry Through Dialogue. *Selcuk Kilinc, Texas A&M University; Tugce Aldemir, Texas A&M University; Vivek Sabanwar, Texas A&M University; Ali Bicer, Texas A&M University; Donggil Song, Texas A&M University*

Using Machine Learning Models to Predict Normalized Learning Gains of High-School Students Playing a Simulation Game-Based Learning Environment. *Matthew Moreno, University of Central Florida; Megan Wiedbusch, University of Central Florida; Barrie Robinson, University of Idaho; Terrance Soule; Justin Riggs, University of Idaho; Roger Azevedo, University of Central Florida*

Chair: *Idowu David Awoyemi, University of Alabama*

38.021. Climate Emotion, Agency, and Justice in Formal and Informal Settings. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Structured Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 515B; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

1. Sentipensar [Feel-Thinking] Cultivates Scientific Sensemaking and Worldbuilding Within and Beyond Ecological Despair (Poster 1). *Kelsie Fowler, University of Washington*

2. Towards and Away: Intersections of Emotion and Ideology along Trajectories of Learning within a Museum Exhibit about Climate Change (Poster 2). *Lynne Zummo, University*

- of Utah; Jordan Giron, University of Utah; Kaitlyn Kinshella, University of Utah; Ajla Aufer, University of Utah; Benjamin A. Janney, University of Utah
3. On “Heaviness”, Racialized Emotions, and “Big” Emergencies: Community Knowledge and Education for Social Justice Amid Climate Coloniality (Poster 3). Noemi Waight, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Wonyong Park, University of Southampton; Jennifer Tripp, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Fatemeh Mozaffari, University at Buffalo - SUNY
 4. Remembering Plant-Human Kin Relations & Supporting Indigenous Youth Wellbeing (Poster 4). Nicole Barry, University of California - Los Angeles; Megan Bang, Northwestern University
 5. “Relatives with Emotions”: Relationality, Responsibility, and Climate Change in a Maya Tzotzil Muslim Community (Poster 5). Lama Ziad Jaber, Florida State University; Ayesha Khurshid, Florida State University; Anairis de la Cruz Benito, Florida State University; Melba Marin-Velasquez, Florida State University; Katherine Murray Yaun, Florida State University
 6. Countering Heat Islands, Planting Trees: Studies of Schoolyards as Habitats for Climate-Just Learning (Poster 6). Kathryn Lanouette, William & Mary; Meredith Dash, Alliance for the Chesapeake Bay
 7. From Eco-Anxiety to Ecological Resonance: Cultivating Joy in a Photovoice Climate Curriculum (Poster 7). Imogen Herrick, University of Kansas; Michael A. Lawson, Kansas State University; Jaclyn Lauren Dudek, University of Kansas
 8. From detached knowledge to embodied care: Cultivating affective textures of collective care in sustainability education (Poster 8). Alfredo Jornet Gil, Universitat de Girona; Hanna Rokenes, University of Oslo; Eliana Mercedes Bussi, University of Girona
 9. Designing for Mobilizing Climate Emotion to Collective Action in High School Chemistry (Poster 9). Minjung Shin, University of California - Irvine; Hosun Kang, University of California - Irvine; Symone Gyles, University of California - Irvine; Issac Li, University of California - Irvine
 10. Undergraduates’ Imaginings for Climate Justice Teaching: Exploring Relationships Across Nature, Constructive Hope, and Meaningful Action (Poster 10). Devon Azzam, University of California - Santa Barbara; Kaylee Allison Laub, University of California - Santa Barbara; Julie Bianchini, University of California - Santa Barbara; Danielle B. Harlow, University of California - Santa Barbara; Karin Lohwasser, University of California - Santa Barbara
 11. Climate Justice and Emotional Growth: Preservice Teachers’ Journey From Climate Overwhelm to Teaching Empowerment (Poster 11). Amal Ibourek, Florida State University; Sukanya Chakraborty, Florida State University; Patrick Sonde, Florida State University
 12. Speculative Climate Action: Supporting Teachers and Students to Imagine More Just and Sustainable Futures

(Poster 12). Nguyen Huynh, West Contra Costa Unified School District; Amanda Nicole Orozco Gonzaga, University of California - Santa Cruz; Jacob Barton, University of California - Berkeley; Emily V. Reigh, University of California - Santa Cruz; Helen Fitzmaurice, University of California - Berkeley

Chairs: Hosun Kang, University of California - Irvine; Lama Ziad Jaber, Florida State University

38.022. The Powerful Role of Adaptive Expertise in Scaffolding Story Comprehension Skills in Young Children. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Symposium

Westin Bonaventure, Level 3, Avalon; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Promoting Narrative Comprehension Skills in At-Risk Children: How does teacher-child interaction matter? Tiia Lindfors, University of Turku; Anu Kajamies, University of Turku; Anne Sorariutta, University of Turku; Mikko Havisto, University of Turku; Aino Mattinen, University of Turku; Janne Lepola, U.S. Department of Education

A Fine-Grained Look at a Coarse-Grained Problem: Effects of Inferential Discussion on Preschoolers’ Thinking. Molly F. Collins, Vanderbilt University

Development Dynamics of Teacher-child Conversations: Findings from Multi-year Teacher Coaching in Dialogic Reading. Janne Lepola, U.S. Department of Education; Anu Kajamies, University of Turku; Tiia Lindfors, University of Turku; Mikko Tiilikainen, University of Turku

Children’s Story Misunderstandings: Opportunities for Fostering Inferential Thinking and Teachers’ Adaptive Responsivity. Molly F. Collins, Vanderbilt University; Joanna Rydberg, Vanderbilt University

Chair: Molly F. Collins, Vanderbilt University

Discussant: Panayiota Kendeou, University of Minnesota

38.023. Methodological Reworlding: Working through (De)Colonial Entanglements. Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Symposium

InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Los Feliz; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Against the Tactical Lie of Coloniality: Personally-at-Stake Academic Dialogues as Decolonial Methodology. Jeong-Eun Rhee, Long Island University - C.W. Post Campus

Writing about Migration: Methodological Dilemmas and Possibilities. Binaya Subedi, The Ohio State University
Translation as Method: Decolonizing Inquiry in Transnational US Funded Research. Sharon S. Subreenduth, Georgia Southern University

Beyond Ruin Porn: Urban Visual Culture and Otherwise Entanglements. Roland Sintos Coloma, Wayne State University

Chair: Jeong-Eun Rhee, Long Island University - C.W. Post

Campus

Discussant: *Roland Sintos Coloma, Wayne State University*

38.024. Robert L. Linn Distinguished Address Award. Division

D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Invited Speaker Session

InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 7th Floor, Hollywood Ballroom I; 2:15-3:45pm

Participant:

Rethinking the Universal Use Hierarchical Linear Modeling.

Daniel F. McCaffrey, Educational Testing Service

Chair: *Jessica Nina Lester, Indiana University*

Speaker: *Daniel F. McCaffrey, Educational Testing Service*

38.025. Simulation as Method, Pedagogy, and Epistemology: A Framework for Monte Carlo Simulation Methods.

Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Symposium

InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Wilshire Grand Ballroom II; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Designing a Simulation Course in the Quantitative Sciences: Lessons Learned. *Zachary K. Collier, University of Connecticut*

Teaching Missing Data Methods through Monte Carlo Simulation. *Kirsten Reyna, University of Connecticut*

From 6Cs to Simulation Studies: A Framework for Teaching Simulation as Methodological Reasoning. *Marcus A. Harris, University of Connecticut*

Chair: *Marcus A. Harris, University of Connecticut*

Discussant: *Eric Loken, University of Connecticut*

38.026. The Nuance of Patterns: Methods for Uncovering Intricate Quantitative Relationships. Division D -

Measurement and Research Methodologies; Paper Session InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Echo Park; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Bridging Scales and Stories: A Joint Factor-Topic Model for Mixed-Format Response Data. *Yuxiao Zhang, Purdue University; David Arthur, University of Washington - Tacoma; Yukiko Maeda, Purdue University; Hua-Hua Chang, Purdue University*

Mapping Educational Inequities Using Bayesian Networks and Spatial Analysis of Social Determinants. *Merve Akin-Tas, University of Kansas*

Mapping Relational Closeness: A New Way to Understand Relationships in Learning Communities. *Seewoo Li, University of California - Los Angeles; Jinwen Luo, University of California - Los Angeles; Minjeong Jeon, University of California - Los Angeles*

Structural After Measurement Estimation for Structural Equation Models with Complex Sampling. *Kyle T. Cox, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Richard G.*

Lambert, University of North Carolina - Charlotte

UMAP-Based Dimensionality Reduction for Educational Data Analysis: Demonstrating Visualization-Informed Clustering Through Student Classification. *Yiran Chen, University of Michigan; Ying Sun, University of Michigan; Peter Riley Bahr, University of Michigan*

Chair: *Yue Di, Michigan State University*

Discussant: *Nathan Alexander, Howard University*

38.027. Beyond the Numbers: Youth Interpreting and Acting on Data for Social Change. Division G - Social Context of

Education; Symposium

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 309; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Data Visualizations for Social Betterment: Youth Developing Self-transcendence in a Data-art Inquiry Program. *Yilang Zhao, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Lynn L. Hodge, University of Tennessee*

Youth Responding to Food Access Data Investigations Through Community Service Action Plans. *Kristin A. Searle, Utah State University; Mengying Jiang, Utah State University; Bolaji R Bamidele, Utah State University; Michaela Harper, Utah State University; Kylie Bell, Utah State University; Emma Griffin, Utah State University*

How Data Investigations Shape Students' Understanding of Air Quality and Inspire Community Action. *Joeeun Shim, Teachers College, Columbia University; Susan A. Yoon, University of Pennsylvania*

Culturally Relevant Data Science: How Youth Interpret Data Regarding Native Language Use and Preservation. *Richard Carlos L. Velasco, University of Florida*

Chairs: *Yilang Zhao, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Kristin A. Searle, Utah State University*

Discussant: *Shiyan Jiang, North Carolina State University*

38.028. Disrupting the Language of Power: Translanguaging, Whiteness, and Educational Futures. Division G - Social

Context of Education; Symposium

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 301A; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Resisting Black Erasure: Raciolinguistic Perspectives and Critical Translanguaging in Bilingual Classrooms. *María Cioe-Pena, University of Pennsylvania*

Unsettling the Roots of Colonial Education Policies:

Unforgetting the Legacy of Indigenous Boarding Schools. *Dee Sherwood, Western Michigan University; Julian Vasquez Heilig, Western Michigan University; Jamie Stuck, Michigan Tribal Legislative Liaison*

Emotional Repertoires: Translanguaging and the psychological costs of internalized whiteness. *Nallely Gecik, University of San Diego; Jennifer A. Chabriel-Amara, University of San Diego; Cheryl E. Matias, University of San Diego*

Reclaiming Voice: Translanguaging as Resistance to the white Listening Subject. *JPB Gerald, Hunter College*
Chair: *Dolores Delgado Bernal, Loyola Marymount University*
Discussant: *Cheryl E. Matias, University of San Diego*

38.029. We Got You, You Got Us:” Workshopping Mentoring Practices within the Social Context of Education. Division G - Social Context of Education; Workshop
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 303B;
2:15-3:45pm

Chair: *Arturo Anaya Servin, University of San Diego*
Participants: *Ayana Allen-Handy, Hofstra University; Patricia Baquedano-Lopez, University of California - Berkeley; Mary B. McVee, University at Buffalo - SUNY*
Discussant: *Antonio Duran, Arizona State University*

38.030. Accountability Systems and State Policy in Education. Division H - Research, Evaluation and Assessment in Schools; Paper Session
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 6th Floor, Metropolitan; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Definitions of Adequate Progress Towards English Proficiency in State Accountability Systems. *Zhaopeng Ding, University of California - Los Angeles; Mark Hansen, University of California - Los Angeles*
Evaluating the Impact of ESSA School Improvement Activities on Academic Outcomes in CSI-Identified Schools: A Regression Discontinuity Case Study. *Russel Potter, Arizona Department of Education*
Leveraging What-If Analysis to Improve Accountability Outcomes for Homeless and Intersecting Student Groups. *Tacey Rodgers, Solano County Office of Education; Joseph Knapp, Solano County Office of Education*

Chair: *Kendall Dwayne Deas, University of South Carolina*
Discussant: *Sandra Barrueco, The Catholic University of America*

38.031. Institutions in Flux: Navigating Institutional Change and Political Tension in Higher Education. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum H; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Survival before Norms? How Universities Decouple from Alliances in Presidential Statements on International Student Support. *YoungHoon Koh, The University of Arizona; Seongjin Park, Speak*
Constructing Compliance and Equity: University Leadership Discourse in Implementing Texas’s Anti-DEI Policy. *Julio J. Mena Bernal, University of Texas at Austin*
Stories from the Frontlines: A Narrative Inquiry of STEM Department Chairs Advancing Equity Amid Political Contention. *Wu Xie, University of Missouri; Candace R. Kuby, University of Missouri*

Gatebreaking in STEM: How Professional Societies Resist DEI Retrenchment through Organizational Strategy and Field-Level Coordination. *Rochelle Williams, University of Southern California; Kendrick B. Davis, University of Southern California*

Chair: *Juan Pedro Ross-Olivares, University of California - Los Angeles*
Discussant: *Valeria G. Dominguez, University of California - Los Angeles*

38.032. Mindsets and Mentorship: Improving Success for Underserved and Community College Students. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum G; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Using QuantCrit to Develop and Examine the Transformational STEM Consciousness Scale. *Juan C. Garibay, University of Virginia; Lindsay Wheeler, University of Virginia*
Do Study-Together Groups Improve Academic Achievement? Evidence from Online Community College Courses. *Jenny Lee, University of California - Irvine; Michael Cooper, University of California - Irvine; Qiujie Li, Nanyang Technological University - National Institute of Education; Waverly Tseng, University of California - Irvine; Di Xu, University of California - Irvine*
A Perfect Match: How Demographic Matching in Peer Mentoring Affects Academic Outcomes. *Kubra Say, Harvard SDP - Office of Educational Quality and Accountability; Nathan J. Daun-Barnett, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Melinda M. Whitford, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

Chair: *Geneva L. Sarcedo, University of Colorado - Denver*
Discussant: *Kevin Eagan, University of California - Los Angeles*

38.033. Understanding Test-Optional Policies and Promise Programs for Educational Equity. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum F; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Examining the Academic Outcomes Associated with Test-Optional Admissions: Evidence from Two Public University Systems. *Kelly Ochs Rosinger, Pennsylvania State University; Dominique Baker, University of Delaware; Joseph Sturm, Pennsylvania State University; Julie J. Park, University of Maryland; Julie Renee Posselt, University of Southern California*
The Impact of Test-Optional Policies on the College Application Process and Academic Experiences Once Enrolled. *Julie J. Park, University of Maryland; Nancy Wong, University of Maryland; Joseph Sturm, Pennsylvania State University; Huong Truong, University of Maryland; Julie Renee Posselt, University of Southern California;*

Dominique Baker, University of Delaware; Kelly Ochs Rosinger, Pennsylvania State University; Carla Partlow, University of Maryland; Angelina Jenkins, University of Maryland

Access and (In)Equity? Administrative Burdens and Institutional Promise Programs. *Kelly Slay, Vanderbilt University; Daniel Hay, Vanderbilt University; Andrew Hunt, Vanderbilt University*

Chair: *Kayla S. Burt, Massachusetts Institute of Technology*

Discussant: *Ozan Jaquette, University of California - Los Angeles*

38.034. (Re)membering Race, Unmasking Power: Socialization and the Futures of Teacher Education Research. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 9; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Racism and Police in Schools: Exploring Pre-Service Teachers' Beliefs. *Hannah Carson Baggett, Auburn University; Kamden Strunk, Virginia Commonwealth University*

Rickety Scaffolding: Teacher Residency Community as Potential Cornerstone for Homeplace in PWIs? *Jocelyn A. Glazier, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Xumei Fan, University of Northern Iowa; Kristin L. Papoi, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Diana B. Lys, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Dana Griffin, Pennsylvania State University; Corey Bray, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Dorothy L. Espelage, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*

The Race Frames of Pre-Service and Novice Teachers of Color. *Leslie Duhaylongsod, Salem State University; Nicole J Harris, Salem State University; Carrie He, Independent Scholar*

Understanding the Success of Black Male Educators in the National Board Certification Process. *Esther Ward, American University; Simone Gibson, Morgan State University; Keisha McIntosh Allen, University of Maryland*

Chair: *Adam J. Alvarez, Texas A&M University*

Discussant: *Sherry L. Deckman, CUNY, Lehman College and Graduate Center*

38.035. Cultivating Teacher Agency & Knowledge: Innovations in STEM/STEAM Professional Development. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 1; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Cultivating Teacher Agency: Professional Development for Culturally Sustaining Environmental STEM Education in South Texas. *Uma Maheshwari Ganesan, University of Texas - Rio Grande Valley; Angela Chapman, University of Texas - Rio Grande Valley; Alexander Hernandez, University of Texas Rio Grande Valley*

Learning Beyond Borders: Experiential Learning and STEM Educators' Teaching Practices. *Diego Lopez, Rice University; Faiza Zafar, Rice University; Mirna Mendoza Wilson, Rice University; Carolyn Nichol, Rice University*

Scaffolded Supports and the Arc of Self-Efficacy in Elementary STEM Teaching. *Tami Lemire, TLC for Educators*

Shaping Identity, Practice and Leadership: NGSS Familiarity and the Impact of Science Teacher Professional Development. *Tess Shirefley, California State University - Monterey Bay; Megan J. Sulsberger, California State University - Monterey Bay; Corin Slown, California State University - Monterey Bay*

A Case Study of STEM Teacher Specialized Knowledge Development Through Peer Feedback and TPACK Framework. *Romario Montaño-Ramos, Texas Tech University; Faith Maina, Texas Tech University; Ngoc Kim Tuyen Pham, Texas Tech University*

Chair: *Kolawole Kushimo, University of Massachusetts - Dartmouth*

Discussant: *Puskar Raj Joshi, Texas A&M University*

38.036. Intersections and Interdependence: Addressing Colonialism, Ableism, and Epistemic Hierarchies in Global Teacher Education. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Symposium JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 6; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Intersections and Interdependence: Addressing Colonialism, Ableism, and Epistemic Hierarchies in Global Teacher Education. *Esther Oyefeso, University of Ibadan*

Addressing Colonialism, Ableism, and Epistemic Hierarchies in Global Teacher Education. *Grace Otinwa, University of Lagos*

Interdependence and Intersections. *Alba Ruth Pinto-Santos, Universidad de La Guajira; Adayenis Bonivento, Universidad de La Guajira; Brunilda Morales, Universidad de La Guajira*

Chair: *Mildred Boveda, Pennsylvania State University*

Discussant: *Ryan L. Shepard, HCT Ventures*

38.037. No Matter How Bleak: Teachers Learning and Living a Justice Praxis. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Symposium JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 8; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

What We Imagine, We Become: Preparing Minoritized and Multilingual Justice-Centered Educators. *Edward R. Curammeng, California State University - Dominguez Hills; Minhye Son, California State University - Dominguez Hills; Sara Jasmin Diaz-Montejano, University of California - Los Angeles*

Sealing the Cracks: A Portrait of Critical Advisement Pedagogy

for Pre-Service Teachers of Color. *Jhey Crisostomo, California State University Dominguez Hills*

Navigational Capital and Critical Race Teacher Mentorship: Duo-Ethnographies of Teacher Mentors. *Marlene Espinoza, Environmental Charter High School - Gardena; Jose Lopez, Environmental Charter High School - Gardena*

Chair: *Melissa Arabel Navarro, San Diego State University*
Discussant: *Cati V. de los Rios, University of California - Berkeley*

38.038. Re-envisioning YA Book Clubs as a Culturally Sustaining Literacy Method for Transforming Teaching and Learning. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 7; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Pláticas, YA Books, and Teacher Identity Building: A Book Club as Teacher Professional Development. *Monica Baldonado-Ruiz, San Diego State University*
Pre-Service Educators Re-imagining Teaching through YAL Book Clubs. *Sandra Saco, Arizona State University*
“Reading Just to Read”: Secondary Students’ Perspectives on YA Book Clubs in an ELA Classroom. *Sybil Durand, University of Arizona*

Chair: *Katherine M. Sciarba, University of Georgia*
Discussant: *Jody N. Polleck, Hunter College - CUNY*

38.039. Reimagining Assessment and Pedagogy: Equity, Justice, and Innovation in Teacher Preparation. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 2; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Good Hearts, Growing Minds: Novice Teachers’ Understanding of Culturally Sustaining Pedagogy in GYO Programs. *Christine Quince, Santa Clara University; Travis J. Bristol, University of California - Berkeley*
Grow Your Own Programs: Tailored designs to support readiness, belonging and student outcomes. *Sunyoung Yoon, Independent Consultant; Conra D. Gist, University of Houston; Jason Greenberg Motamedi, Education Northwest*
Investigating M.Ed. students’ perception of the authenticity of their curriculum assessments in Mainland China. *YIYUN ZHANG, University of Bristol*
Reimagining Teacher Education During Troubled Times: Building Strong Equity. *Elizabeth Stringer Keefe, Stonehill College; Rebekah C. Louis, Stonehill College*
(Re)imagining Teacher Education Performance Assessments from a Justice and Equity Perspective. *Carol M. Adams, Seattle University; Ana M. Rivero Arias, Seattle University; Colleen Loranger, Seattle University*

Chair: *Jessica N. Hiltabidel, George Mason University*
Discussant: *Connor Warner, University of Utah*

38.040. Language, Borders, and Belonging: Multilingual Futures and Immigrant Students. Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 10; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Bilingualism and Cultural Competence: A Systematic Review of Trends, Methodologies, and Evolving Perspectives. *Arwa Alkhawaja, San Diego State University; Christopher Brum, San Diego State University*
Religious and Political Discourse on Immigration: A Case Study of a Red-Zone Community in New Mexico. *Jenna Doane, The University of New Mexico; Yi-Shan Li, The University of Texas System; Gretchen Ponder, University of New Mexico*
Education Policies and the Structural Exclusion of Newcomers Immigrant Students in California. *Carolyn Sattin-Bajaj, University of California - Santa Barbara*
Reclaiming Voice, Resisting Silence: Reimagining Multilingual Futures through a Duo-autoethnographic Study of Tanzania’s Language-in-Education Policy. *Donather Daudi Magabe, University of North Carolina - Greensboro; Scholastika Paul Massawe, University of Massachusetts - Amherst*
Restorative Conflict Resolution with Multilingual Students: Beyond Translation. *Tina Ahmadi, Ball State University; Kiah Taylor, Ball State University; Serena J. Salloum, Ball State University*

Chair: *Miguel Angel Garcia-Bocanegra, Northwestern University*
Discussant: *Gabriela López, Stanford University*

SIG Sessions

38.041. AI and Action Research: Coding Robots, Literacy, Youth-led, Assessment, Tensions and Possibilities. SIG-Action Research; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Plaza III; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

A Collaborative Action Research on Integrating Coding Robots to Support Children’s Play and Teacher’s Learning. *Heesoo Woo, Ohio State University; Minyoung Gil, Kent State University*
AI in Action Research: Muzzle or Megaphone? Voice, Power, and Pedagogy in Youth-Led Inquiry. *Dane Stickney, University of Colorado - Denver; Allison JoAnn Lester, Arizona State University*
Exploring AI Literacy: Student Perceptions of Learning, Ethics, and Use in the Classroom. *Macie Barrett, Florida Atlantic University; Michelle Vaughan-McGovern, Florida Atlantic University; Melissa Antonelli, Florida Atlantic University*
Rethinking Assessment and Generative AI: Teachers Imagining a Critical Digital Humanist Success Paradigm for a New Era.

Christine Balt, University of Toronto Schools; Kimberley MacKinnon, University of Toronto Schools; Natalie Cannistraro, University of Toronto Schools; Alan Kraguljac, University of Toronto Schools; Isabella Liu, Branksome Hall; Melissa Shaddick, University of Toronto Schools

Tensions and Possibilities of Generative AI in Futuring Kindergarten Learning through Action Research. *Wai Ming Cheung, University of Hong Kong; Serene Chan, University of Hong Kong*

Discussant: *Merve Basdogan, Texas Tech University*

38.042. Civic Practices, Education Policy and Diverse

Perspectives. SIG-Adolescence and Youth Development; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 301B;
2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

How Identity-Based Youth Programs Shape Civic Behavior Among Disadvantaged Adolescents: A Network Co-evolution Approach. *Maneeza Dawood, Stanford University*

Investigating Adolescents' Openness to the Opposing View. *Tenelle Porter, Rowan University; Jon M. Valant, Brookings; Daniel Newark, HEC Paris*

Navigating English-Dominant Schooling: Bi/Multilingual Students' Responses to Raciolinguistic Ideologies. *Thaina Ferrari Deolindo, University of Arizona*

Parental Rights and Youth Epistemic Restriction on the Moms for Liberty Podcast. *June Jackson, University of Washington*

Transnational Lives, Local Schools: Institutional Responses to Immigrant Youth in Puebla, Mexico. *Alex Koenig, University of Chicago*

Chair: *Rosie Ojeda, California Polytechnic State University - San Luis Obispo*

38.043. Multiple Selves in Educational Contact Zones: East Asian Academic Experiences Through Dialogical Self Theory.

SIG-Asian Americans and Pacific Islanders in Education and Research; Working Group Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 501A;
2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Wobbling Forward: Vulnerability and Multiple Selves of Transnational Researchers. *Eun Bee Ellin Kim, Think & Write / Pacific College of Health and Sciences; Jing Du, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Me, Myself, and (A)I: The Confessions of Teenagers. *Justin Lee, Think & Write; Khloe Hong, THINK & WRITE; Lilian Zhou, Think & Write*

Whose Story Gets Told?: Adult Perspectives on Minority Underrepresentation in High School US History. *Ethan Yeung, Youth Teams in Education Research; Caryn Seulah Cho, Youth Teams in Education Research; Khloe Hong, THINK & WRITE*

Silent I-Positions: Dialogical Exploration of Cultural and

Societal Influences on Student Classroom Participation. *Khloe Hong, THINK & WRITE; Yifan Zhang, Think & Write; Lilian Zhou, Think & Write; Molly Hong, Think & Write*

38.044. Bilingual Education Research SIG Mentor Session: "We Are Not Alone": Building Solidarity, Community, and Collective Power. SIG-Bilingual Education Research; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 403B;
2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Mentorship Session. *Jiadi Zhang, University of Missouri - St. Louis*

BER SIG Mentoring Session. *Kyungjin Hwang, University of South Carolina*

BER SIG Mentor Session. *Wenyang Sun, University of Utah*

Chairs: *Jiadi Zhang, University of Missouri - St. Louis; Kyungjin Hwang, University of South Carolina; Qinchun Li, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

38.045. Infusing Healing Energy into Education: Daoist, Buddhist, and Confucian Insights. SIG-Confucianism, Taoism, Buddhism and Education; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 501C;
2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Chinese Philosophical Therapies and Inner Healing. *Leonard J. Waks, Qufu Normal University, Shandong China*

From Mud to Lotus: Transforming Dukkha into a Pedagogy of Love. *Gaston Esteban Bacquet, University of Glasgow*

Harmonizing as Healing, Pedagogical Attunement: A Daoist Approach. *Hongyu Wang, Oklahoma State University - Tulsa*

Friends, Fools, and Foes: Restorative Buddhist Paradox and Transformation. *Jin Jr Shi, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Daoism as an Intellectual Sanctuary of Healing for Personal and Social Cultural Trauma. *Xin Li, California State University - Long Beach*

Returning to Who We Truly Are: Cultivating Qi Life Force for Healing Self and World. *Jing Lin, University of Maryland*

Chair: *Xin Li, California State University - Long Beach*

Discussant: *Hongyu Wang, Oklahoma State University - Tulsa*

38.046. Advancing Critical Education of Muslim Students and Scholars: Social Justice Research in Community. SIG-Critical Educators for Social Justice; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304B;
2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

MusCrit in Practice: Muslim American Women's Educational Counter-Narratives as Social Justice Pedagogy. *Noor Ali, Northeastern University*

Disrupting Inequities in Education: Centering Muslim Student Voices for Socially Just Schools. *Sahar Khawaja, University of Denver*

Muslim Teens Got Faith: Narratives of spirituality, resistance, and identity among middle and high schoolers. *Amaarah N. DeCuir, American University*

“I Am a STEM Muslimah”: Exploring STEM Identity Formation among Muslim Women Undergraduates through MusCrit and Participatory Action Research. *Vivian Zohery, University of Maryland*

Critical Race Praxis in Language Education: An Autoethnographic Study of International Muslim Scholars in the U.S. *Fatima Seyma Kizil, Syracuse University; Ibrahim Kizil, Syracuse University*

Present, Yet Invisible: Exploring the Experiences of Muslim Women Faculty in U.S. Higher Education Institutions. *Hina Rehman, Rutgers University*

Chair: *Amaarah N. DeCuir, American University*

Discussant: *Carolyn M. Lane, California State University - Bakersfield*

38.047. Reimagining Black Masculinities: Exploring the Educational Experiences of Black Boys and Men. SIG-Critical Examination of Race, Ethnicity, Class and Gender in Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 3; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Educational Emasculation and the Reimagining of Black Boyhood. *Giovanni E. Whyte, University of North Dakota*

Can Black Boys Be Children: Towards a Black Boy Innocence in K-12 Schools. *Andre Spencer Anderson-Thompson, University of California - Davis*

Navigating Space, Place, and Belonging: Intersections of Identity, Community, and Progressive Masculinities at Predominantly White Institutions. *Jonathan Berhanu, Hobart & William Smith Colleges*

“I’m Learning How to Be Who I Am”: Exploring Masculinities Among College Men of Color. *Derrick R. Brooms, Morehouse College*

Academic Armor: Black Male Faculty and the Exhaustion of Racial Battle Fatigue. *Edwin Nii Bonney, Clemson University; Antonio L. Ellis, American University; Darryl Corey, Radford University*

Chairs: *Tara Marie Brown, University of Maryland; Jordan Bell, University of Maryland*

Discussant: *Tara Marie Brown, University of Maryland*

38.048. Anti-Racism in Early Childhood Education. SIG-Critical Perspectives on Early Childhood Education; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304C; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Disrupting Whiteness Through an Early Childhood Teacher Educator Critical Community of Practice. *Azaria I. Cunningham, Boston University; Allison Sterling Henward, Pennsylvania State University; Quiana M. Jackson, Bermuda Ministry of Education; Michelle N. Brown, Pennsylvania State University*

Using Anti-Racist Pedagogy in EC Teacher Preparation Programs. *Oona Fontanella-Nothom, California State University - Dominguez Hills; Amanda Welch, California State University - Los Angeles; Juliette Marie Lahey, Community Action Partnership San Luis Obispo*

Creating a Blueprint for Eliminating Suspensions, Expulsions, and Exclusions in Early Education in North Carolina. *Sherrell Hicklen House, University of North Carolina - Greensboro; Valerie Jarvis McMillan, North Carolina A&T State University; Nina Smith, North Carolina Central University; Jennifer Mendoza Beasley, North Carolina A&T State University; Megan Vinh, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Brenda K. Williamson, State of North Carolina*

Using Digital Images to Foster Resistance in Early Childhood Classrooms. *Nakisha D. Whittington, Stanford University*
An Autoethnographic Afrofuturist Experience of Dance Education. *Quiana M. Jackson, Bermuda Ministry of Education*

Chair: *Kerry-Ann Escayg, University of Nebraska - Omaha*

Discussant: *Flora Farago, Stephen F. Austin State University*

38.049. Innovative Intervention Approaches to Promote Holistic Well-Being, Competence, and Retention of Early Childhood Educators. SIG-Early Education and Child Development; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Georgia II; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Wage Supports in Early Care and Education: Educator Perspectives on Relief and Remaining Needs. *Yoonjeon Kim, University of California - Berkeley; Wanzi Muruvi, University of California - Berkeley; Anna Powell, University of California - Berkeley*

Promoting a Culture of Care: Organization-level Variation in the Impact of Well-Being First on Head Start Educators’ Well-Being. *Lieny Jeon, University of Virginia; Shuai Li, University of Virginia; Xiangyu Zhao, University of Virginia; Sarah Chapman, University of Virginia*

Head Start Educators’ Well-being: Impact Results from a Cluster Randomized Controlled Trial of a Holistic Wellness Intervention. *Timothy G. Ford, University of Oklahoma; Kyong-Ah Kwon, University of Oklahoma; Carolyn Cheema, University of Oklahoma Health Sciences Center; Mia Kile, University of Oklahoma; Hongwu Wang, University of Florida*

Chair: *Kyong-Ah Kwon, University of Oklahoma*

Discussant: *Sara E. Rimm-Kaufman, University of Virginia*

38.050. Reimaging Environmental Learning for Justice and Equity. SIG-Environmental Education; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 506;
2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Climate Change Education and Teachers' Working Conditions: Teachers' Exposure to Heat Stress in Brazil. *Inny Accioly, Universidade Federal Fluminense; Igor Andrade da Costa, Universidade Federal Rural do Rio de Janeiro; Luciane Silva Nascimento, State University of Rio de Janeiro*

"Leveraging diversity and maximizing productivity:" Discourses of interest convergence in marine and climate science institutions. *Marisa Lally, Georgia Southern University; Christina W. Yao, University of South Carolina; Chrystal A. George Mwangi, George Mason University; Vijay Kanagala, Salem State University; Jennifer Michelle Johnson, Temple University; Onjale Scott Price, George Mason University; Eunjin Han, George Mason University*

The Rhizome of Environmental and Climate Justice Education: A semi-autoethnographic systematic literature review. *Dinorah-Marie Hudson, Graduate Center - CUNY*

Toward Ecological Justice in Urban Green Spaces: Engaging Secondary Students Through Walking. *Jennifer A. Vadeboncoeur, University of British Columbia; Natacha Monestel-Mora, University of British Columbia; Auralia Brooke, University of New Brunswick; Kristiina Kumpulainen*

Integrating Environmental and Ethnic Studies Through a Social Justice Outdoor Education Program for High School Learners. *Laura Moorhead, San Francisco State University; Jeremy D. Jimenez, SUNY - College at Cortland*

Chair: *Richard V. Kahn, Antioch University*

Discussant: *Patience Amadu, University of Colorado - Colorado Springs*

38.051. Preparing Educators to Work with Culturally Diverse and Multilingual Families. SIG-Family, School, Community Partnerships; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Atrium II;
2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

"Like what Guadalupe Valdés says: we aren't experts, parents are!": Ethnography, PBL and Teacher Education. *Jen Stacy, University of New Mexico*

Unpacking Father Engagement in Teacher Preparation: Views, Biases, and Opportunities. *Kyle Elizabeth Miller, Illinois State University; Jordan Arellanes, Illinois State University; Watsachol Narongsaksakul, Illinois State University*

Reimagining Justice-Centered Teacher Preparation: Preservice Teachers' Transformative Engagement with Multilingual Children and Families. *Gumiko Monobe, Kent State University; Jennifer Anne McCreight, Kent State University; Bee Viton, Kent State University*

A Place in Between: Navigating Community-based Language Education and K-12 Schools as Iranian Immigrant Parents. *Yalda M. Kaveh, Arizona State University; Sepide Pazhouhi, Arizona State University; Roya Fathalizadeh, Arizona State University; Yaxin Wang, Arizona State University*

Cracked Spaces, Flint Stones, and Diamonds: Teachers' Perceptions of Marginalized Students' Homes. *Shlomit Demsky-Cohen, The Hebrew University of Jerusalem*

Chair: *Yetunde S. Alabede, Michigan State University*

Discussant: *Jacqueline Lynch, Florida International University*

38.052. Disrupted Belonging: Graduate Students Confront Equity and Exclusion. SIG-Graduate and Postdoctoral Education across the Disciplines; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum I;
2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Becoming While Black: Examining the Socialization Experiences and Meaning-Making Processes of Black Men Pursuing PhDs in Higher Education at Historically White Institutions. *Dalvin Trevon Dunn, Texas A&M University; Credric Freeman, Texas A&M University; Kenuantae Storey, Texas A&M University; Samuel A Evans, Texas A&M University*

In This Room, We Were Seen: Autoethnographic Reflections of Doctoral Women of Color. *Sherell A. McArthur, University of Georgia; Mya Lynn Seay Milner, University of Georgia; Rosangela Araujo Silva, University of Georgia; Gyu Lim Choi, University of Georgia*

Signals of Identity Safety: How Relational and Curricular Cues Shape Belonging for Graduate Students of Color. *Royel M. Johnson, University of Southern California; Mya Haynes, USC; Terrell Lamont Strayhorn, Virginia Union University*

Students Navigating the Impacts of Anti-DEI Laws on Their Experiences in Racial/Ethnic Graduate Student Organizations. *Jarett D. Haley, University of Delaware; Amber Williams, University of Michigan; Abigail Quick, University of Delaware; Sadé S. Williams, University of Delaware*

For us by us: Horizontal peer mentorship as a pathway to Blackwomen's doctoral completion. *Brittany L. Marshall, San Diego State University; Dana Michelle Harris, Independent Scholar; Jameelah R Wright, William Paterson University*

Chair: *Elaine Jessica Castillo Tamargo, California State University - Long Beach*

Discussant: *Cassandra Victoria Guzman, Cornell University*

38.053. Educational Policy, Reforms, and Change in the Middle East and North Africa Towards Social Justice, Equity, and Political Inclusion. SIG-International Studies; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304A;
2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Educational Policy and Reform in the MENA Region: Between Crisis and Possibility. *Selahattin Turan, Bursa Uludag University; Khalid Husny Arar, Texas State University; Mohammed Elmeski, Sigma Associates Incorporated Minnesota*

Implementing and Improving Inclusive Strategies for Equity in Education: Politics as Praxis in Turkish Educational Environment. *Hamit Ozen, Eskisehir Osmangazi University; Taner Atmaca, Duzce University; Metin Ozkan, Gaziantep University; PINAR YAVUZ, Ministry of National Education, TÜRKİYE*

The Path to a Knowledge-Based Economy through Reforming Public K-12 Education: Educational Policies and Educator Professional Development in Saudi Arabia. *Hana Alzandi Alghamdi, University of Denver; Julia Mahfouz, University of Colorado - Denver*

Private and International School Policies in Arab Countries: Rethinking Educational Equity and Cultural Identity. *Rania Sawalhi, University of Jordan*

Educational Policies in Wars, Conflict and Emergencies: Cases from the MENA Region. *Khalid Husny Arar, Texas State University; Soheil Salha, An-Najah National University; Ahmed Tlili, Beijing Normal University*

Chair: *Selahattin Turan, Bursa Uludag University*

Discussant: *Khalid Husny Arar, Texas State University*

38.054. Games as Dialogues Between Pasts and Futures:

Playing Toward Educational Reimagination. SIG-Media, Culture, and Learning; Symposium

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum J; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Examining the Role of Playful Games in Foundational English Literacy Instruction for Adolescent Refugee Girls. *Beth Krone, Kennesaw State University; Hannah Edber, The Global Village Project*

Experimenting with AI Ethics: Youth Reasoning in the AI Audit Card Game. *Vishesh Kumar, Northwestern University; Sarah Burriss, Vanderbilt University; Safinah Ali, Massachusetts Institute of Technology; Yelena Janumyan, Vanderbilt University; Angela Eeds, Vanderbilt Collaborative for STEM Education and Outreach*

Tracing Chronotopic Laminations around “Troublemaking” Through a Reflective Roleplaying Activity for Pre/In-Service Teachers. *Karis Michelle Jones, Baylor University; Zia Pochkhanawala, Baylor University; Virginia Killian Lund, University of Rhode Island*

“You Can Create an Authentic Experience”: Teacher Desires and Tensions Around Classroom Game Implementation. *Hannah Dietrich, Sam Houston State University; Virginia Killian Lund, University of Rhode Island; Karis Michelle Jones, Baylor University; Joshua Jonas, Baylor University*

Negotiating Play: A Discourse Analysis of Paired Videogame

Play. *Laurie "Darian" Thrailkill, East Carolina University; Hannah Dietrich, Sam Houston State University*

Negotiating Rules, Roles, and Ideologies in Children's Narrative Gameplay. *Alex Corbitt, Syracuse University; Mariana Lima Becker, University of Georgia*

Chair: *Luna Laliberte, Stanford University*

Discussant: *Tracy J. Fullerton, University of Southern California*

38.055. From Classmates to Friends: Understanding Peers'

Role in Student Motivation. SIG-Motivation in Education; Symposium

Westin Bonaventure, Level 2, Beverly; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Which Peers' Mindsets Matter in the Undergraduate STEM Classroom? *Nathaniel Woznicki, New York University; Lois Drage, Cardiff University; Katherine M. Muenks, University of Texas at Austin*

Fixed Mindset-Signaling Peer Behaviors in STEM Classrooms. *Eunjin Seo, Texas State University; So Yeon Lee, The University of Alabama at Birmingham*

Students' Social Positioning in the Classroom and Their Perceptions of Teachers' Academic and Social Goals. *Alla Hemi, University of Haifa; Adar Ben-Eliyahu, University of Haifa; Martin Daumiller, Ludwig Maximilian University of Munich*

Peer Recognition and Math Identity Development: A Longitudinal Network Perspective. *William Van Luven, Michigan State University; Utku Caybas, Michigan State University; Jennifer Watling Neal, Michigan State University; Zachary P. Neal, Michigan State University; Lisa Linnenbrink-Garcia, Michigan State University*

From Conversations to Comparisons: The Importance of Peers for Math Motivation. *Utku Caybas, Michigan State University; Ada Fulin Ergun, Yeditepe University; Lisa Linnenbrink-Garcia, Michigan State University*

Chairs: *Utku Caybas, Michigan State University; Alla Hemi, University of Haifa; Martin Daumiller, Ludwig Maximilian University of Munich; Lisa Linnenbrink-Garcia, Michigan State University*

Discussant: *Ellen L. Usher, Mayo Clinic*

38.056. Measuring and Addressing Gaps in Out-of-School

Time Access: Barriers, Data Infrastructure, and Program Impacts. SIG-Out-of-School Time; Symposium Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 409AB; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Measuring Supply and Demand for Expanded Learning Programs. *Patricia Burch, University of Southern California; Jon Fullerton, University of Southern California; Marshall Garland, Gibson Consulting Group, Inc.; Alvin Makori, University of Southern California; Amie Rapaport, University of Southern California; Anna R. Saavedra, University of Southern California; Kelly Sarmiento,*

University of Southern California; Daniel Silver, University of Southern California; Marco Torres, University of Southern California

Who's Left Out? Investigating Barriers to Afterschool Program Participation Across Two Decades. *Nikki Yamashiro, Afterschool Alliance*

Implementation and Impact of a No-Cost District Summer School Program. *Jennifer McMurrer, Southern Methodist University; Marshall Garland, Gibson Consulting Group, Inc.; Amie Rapaport, University of Southern California; David J. Osman, Gibson Consulting; Amanda Brown Cross, University of Pittsburgh; Courtney Grondziowski, University of Pittsburgh; Tori Nickerson, Gibson Consulting Group*

Chair: *Jon Fullerton, University of Southern California*

Discussants: *Erica Lim, Broad Foundation; Lou Calanche, Expand LA*

38.057. Counter-Storytelling for Queer & Trans Epistemic Justice. SIG-Queer Studies; Symposium
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Los Cerritos; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Gender physics: An autoethnographic essay. *Jared Boland, University of Toronto - OISE*

Navigating Methodological Considerations through Queer and Trans* Epistemologies. *Susanne Nyaga, University of Toronto - OISE*

Thinking Queerly with Educational Futurities. *Madeleine Long Long, University of Toronto - OISE*

Building Our Capacities to Breathe Through Queer and Trans Epistemologies. *Alexander Vesuna, University of Toronto - OISE*

The Traumatophilic Wound That Remains Is What Teaches: Carving a Queer Kinky Otherwise- Through Lorde and Michelangelo's David. *Maclean Frey, University of Toronto - OISE*

Chair: *Qui Alexander, University of Toronto*

Discussant: *Loretta LeMaster, University of Toronto - OISE*

38.058. Race, Equity, and Inclusion in K-12 and College Athletic Spaces. SIG-Research Focus on Education and Sport; Paper Session

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Los Feliz; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Excluded on the Sidelines: Latina/o/x Administrators in NCAA Division I Institutions. *Guillermo Ortega, Texas Tech University; Jon McNaughtan, Texas Tech University*

"If I hadn't played sports": Critical Narratives from Former Compton Students on School-based Team Sports. *Nansi Reyes, California State University - Long Beach; Maiyoua Vang, California State University - Long Beach*

An Open Secret in Sport: Exploring Mental Health and Coping of Black High School Coaches. *Jessica Moore, University of Georgia*

Analyzing Navigational Capital Discrepancies Towards a More Equitable Vision for Name, Image and Likeness Policies.

Isaiah Simmons, RAND Corporation

Present! A Systematic Review of Latina/o/x Identity in College Athletics. *Guillermo Ortega, Texas Tech University; Nikola Grafnetterova, University of Colorado - Boulder*

Chair: *Agustín J. García, Texas A&M University—Corpus Christi*

38.059. Analyzing Mathematical Experiences in Higher Education: Undergraduate and Graduate Perspectives.

SIG-Research in Mathematics Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum A; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Analyzing Undergraduate Experiences with Primary Source Projects in Mathematics through Learning Experience Network Analysis. *Ananya Mahesh, University of Alabama - Birmingham; Latham Girona, University of Alabama - Birmingham; Kathleen Michelle Clark, University of Alabama - Birmingham; Jonan Phillip Donaldson, University of Alabama - Birmingham*

Evaluating the Effectiveness of Multiple Solution Methods for Undergraduate Trinomial Factoring Performance. *Eunmi Joung, Utah Valley University; Mia Kang, Utah Valley University; B. Jasmine Park, American Institutes for Research*

Fostering a Critical Stance Through Inquiry: Transforming Future Teachers' Perspectives in an Upper-Division Mathematics Course. *Jaime Santos, San Diego State University; Ruo Ning (Nancy) Qiu, San Diego State University; Debra Carney, Colorado School of Mines; Nicholas Fortune, Western Kentucky University; Nicholas Jacome, San Diego State University; Chris L. Rasmussen, San Diego State University*

Mathematical Modeling in College Algebra: Exploring Assumptions, Pedagogical Approaches, and Effects on Student Success. *Reinaldo Ponce, Florida Atlantic University; Sabrina F. Sembiente, Florida Atlantic University*

Chair: *Jessica McCormick, University of Pittsburgh - Greensburg*

38.060. Evaluation of the Impact of Interventions and School Characteristics on Reading and Literacy Achievement.

SIG-Research in Reading and Literacy; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Beaudry A; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Does UPSTART Program Elevate Early Literacy Attainment of Utah Kids? *Kerong Wu; Wynn Shooter, Utah Education Policy Center; Jingshun Zhang, Florida Gulf Coast University*

Evaluation of a Statewide Early Literacy Coaching Institute: A Focus on Coaching Conversations. *Jeanne Schulte, Oakland University; Stacy Brazell, Port Huron Area Schools; Melissa A. Bishop, Oakland University; Julie Joann Ricks-Doneen,*

Oakland University; Patricia Schobloher, Oakland University; Tomoko Wakabayashi, Oakland University; Paola Andrea Guerrero-Rosada, University of California - Irvine

SUPR Schools: Systems for Uncorrelating Poverty and Reading in North Carolina Elementary Schools. Amy Walter, North Carolina State University; Dennis S. Davis, North Carolina State University; Jill F. Grifenhagen, North Carolina State University; Janell A. Miller, North Carolina State University; Jill S Jones, North Carolina State University; Lesley Wirt, North Carolina State University

Making Thinking Visible: Metacognitive Teacher Talk and Literacy Growth for Upper Elementary Multilingual Learners. Haleema Khalil, North Carolina State University; Jackie E. Rehyea, North Carolina State University; Dennis S. Davis, North Carolina State University; Xinyan Fu, North Carolina State University; Corrie Dobis, North Carolina State University; Bethany P. Lewis, University of Alabama; Becky H. Huang, The Ohio State University

Effects of a Multicomponent Intervention in Upper-Elementary Grades: Findings from a Quasi-Experiment and Conceptual Replication. John Z. Strong, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Laura S. Tortorelli, Michigan State University; Blythe E. Anderson, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Eunsoo Cho, University of California - Riverside

Chair: John Z. Strong, University at Buffalo - SUNY

Discussant: Zoi Traga-Philippakos, University of Tennessee

38.061. Black Mothership within and Beyond the Academy: Reconceptualizing Radical Futurity. SIG- Research on Women and Education; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 504;
2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Conceptualizing Spirituality in Critical Race Mothering Within and Beyond the Academy. Larissa Malone, University of North Carolina - Wilmington

We Ain't Going If She Can't Come With Me: An Auto-ethnography of a Black Single Mama who Walked Across EVERY Stage with her Daughter. Daphanie N. Bibbs, University at Buffalo - SUNY

Black Mothership Figuring the Borderlands through Visual Duo-Nkwaethnography. Laura Krystal Porterfield, Rutgers University - Newark; Lynnette Mawhinney, Rutgers University - Newark

Interrogations of the Mythical Norm: Using Endarkened Poetic Inquiry to Queer Black Mothership. Meghan L. Green, Erikson Institute

Looking Back to Move Forward: Unpacking Maternal Misogynoir in the Academy. Crystasany R. Turner, University of Wisconsin - Milwaukee

Chair: Crystasany R. Turner, University of Wisconsin - Milwaukee

Discussant: Venus E. Evans-Winters, The Ohio State University

38.062. Science Teacher Education and Professional Development. SIG-Science Teaching and Learning; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, San Bernardino; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Investigating the Influence of Experiences in the Pandemic Era on a Novice Chemistry Teacher Identity. Mayra Muñoz, Montclair State University

Prospective teachers' development of an epistemic orientation towards teaching science for knowledge generation in an undergraduate environmental science teaching practicum. Matthew James Shackley, University of California - Santa Barbara

Preservice Teachers Earth Science Understandings: Then and Now. Jennifer A. Wilhelm, University of Kentucky; Rebecca McNall Krall, University of Kentucky

Expanding Elementary STEM Education Through Teacher-Researcher Complementarity: A Rural STEM Education Research Case Study. Christine McGrail, University of North Dakota

Chair: Shannon G. Davidson, University of Alabama

38.063. Teaching and Learning with GenAI. SIG-Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis; Paper Session
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 6th Floor, Broadway; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Applying Generative Artificial Intelligence to Task-based Language Teaching and Learning: A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis. Yan Li, The Education University of Hong Kong; Rustam Shadiev, Zhejiang University; Thomas K.F. Chiu, The Chinese University of Hong Kong

Are We Overestimating the Power of Generative AI? A Meta-Analysis of Its Impact on Student Learning. Yijia Yuan, University of Cambridge; Weichao Si, University of Hong Kong

Does Generative Artificial Intelligence Enhance Language Learning? A Meta-Analysis. Jinwen Qu, East China Normal University; Yinuo Li, East China Normal University; Jun Qian, East China Normal University; Jing Leng, East China Normal University; Lixin Ye, East China Normal University

Fostering Learners' Creativity in Human-AI Collaboration: A Review of Instructional Strategies and the Effects of Generative AI. Yuanrong Wang, Beijing Normal University; Jiixin He, Beijing Normal University; Huanhuan Wang, Beijing Normal University

Motivated by Machines? A Meta-Analysis of GenAI's Influence on ESL/EFL Learning Motivation. Meng Xiong, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Timothy Teo, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Yao Yao Ji, Chinese University of Hong Kong

38.064. Crafting, Leaving, and Organizing: Understanding

Teachers' Work in Precarious Times. SIG-Teachers Work/Teacher Unions; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 501B;
2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Generalizability and Determinants of Teacher Job Crafting Profiles Across Teaching Levels: A Job Demands-Resources Perspective. *Chan Wang, The Education University of Hong Kong; Xianhan Huang, The Education University of Hong Kong; Shiyu Zhang, University of Hong Kong*
Public Wins: Rank-and-File Unionism, Participatory Democracy, and Teacher Organizing for the Long Haul in Massachusetts. *Noelle Mapes, Graduate Center - CUNY*
Why Teachers Leave and Will They Teach Again: A Latent Profile Analysis of Workplace Concerns. *Xiaobo Wei, University of South Carolina; Angela D. Starrett, University of South Carolina; Ruiqin Gao, University of South Carolina*
"We're On the Front Lines": Two Decades of Teacher Organizing in New Orleans. *Riley Collins, University of California - Santa Cruz*

38.065. Advancing Multimodal Analytics to Capture Classroom-Based Activities. SIG-Technology, Instruction, Cognition & Learning; Symposium
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Santa Barbara C; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Using A Novel Audio-Video Transformer for Classifying Elementary Instructional Activities. *Peter A. Youngs, University of Virginia; Jonathan K. Foster, University at Albany - SUNY; Matthew Korban, University of Virginia; Scott T. Acton, University of Virginia*
Validating Automated Teaching Effectiveness with Multimodal Data. *Tim Fütterer, University of Tübingen; Ruikun Hou, University of Tübingen; Babette Buhler, Technical University of Munich; Efe Bozkir, Technical University of Munich; Courtney A. Bell, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Enkelejda Kasneci, University of Tübingen; Peter Gerjets, University of Tübingen; Ulrich Trautwein, University of Tübingen*
Generalizable AI Models for Classifying Student Collaborative Discourse in Classrooms. *Chelsea Chandler, University of Colorado - Boulder; Sidney K. D'Mello, University of Colorado - Boulder*
Decoding Instructional Dialogue: Human-AI Collaborative Analysis of Teacher Use of AI Tool at Scale. *Alex Liu, University of Washington; William Lief Evison Esbenshade, Google Inc; Shawon Sarkar, University of Washington; Zewei Tian, University of Washington; Zachary Zhang, University of Washington; Kevin He, University of Washington; Min Sun, University of Washington*
AI-Driven Embedded Assessment Agent for Enhancing University Students' Online Collaborative Learning Engagement and Self-Efficacy. *Fa Liu, East China Normal*

University; Dandan Gao, East China Normal University; Haoming Wang, East China Normal University

Chair: *Peter A. Youngs, University of Virginia*

Discussant: *Xiaoming Zhai, University of Georgia*

38.066. Advancing Educators and Education through a Lens of Ethical Care. SIG-Urban Learning, Teaching, and Research; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum C; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Advancing Social Justice in Teacher Education: A Case Study of California Programs. *Tina Duong, San Marino Unified School District; Sharon H. Ulanoff, California State University - Los Angeles*
Building Cultural Trust: Relational Pedagogy and the Education of Black Boys in an Urban Charter School. *Stuart Rhoden, Arizona State University*
Conceptions of Culture in Urban HBCU Teacher Preparation. *Wyletta S. Gamble-Lomax, Coppin State University*
No Challenge Too Great: High-Performing California Urban Educators' Community of Care Framework. *Teri A. Marcos, National University; Wayne Padover, National University; Donald Wise, National University; William Loose, National University; Susan Belenardo, National University*
Through Their Eyes: Centering Black Student Voice to Reimagine Affirming Teacher Dispositions. *Virginia S. Redwine Johnson, Texas A&M University; John A. Williams, Texas A&M University*

Chair: *Terence L Mayo, New York University*

38.067. The Potential of English Language Arts Education for Restor(y)ing Hopeful Socioecological Futures. SIG-Writing and Literacies; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Plaza II; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Expansive learning with youth: Exploring student inquiries into local and global ecosystems. *Jill M. Castek, University of Arizona; Michael Manderino, Northern Illinois University*
Drawing Rights to (Re)Story Ecological Wrongs: Tracing the Shape of Children's "Voice" in Communicating the Climate Crisis. *Jon M. Wargo, University of Michigan; Cassie J. Brownell, University of Toronto; Kathleen Schenkel, San Diego State University*
Restorying Preservice ELA Teachers' Beliefs about Climate Literacy Pedagogy. *Stephanie Rollag Yoon, Minnesota State University - Mankato; Jana Lo Bello Miller, University of Minnesota*
Visual (Re)Storying of Climate Images in the Literacy Classroom: Developing a Model for Climate Literacy Development with Preservice Teachers. *Julianna E. Lopez Kershen, University of Oklahoma; Kristy Brugar, University of Oklahoma*

Understanding immigrant children's transnational knowledges about global climate change literacies. *Faythe Beauchemin, Boston College; Brenda Luo, Boston College; Li Yong, Boston College; Geying Zhang, Boston College*

Coupling Imagination with Action for Sustainable Energy Transitions: Middle School Students Place-Based Authoring of the Future. *Michelle Jordan, Arizona State University; Steven J. Zuiker, Arizona State University*

Chair: *Alexandra Panos, University of South Florida*

Discussants: *Alexandra Panos, University of South Florida; Rebecca Woodard, University of Illinois at Chicago*

Division and SIG Roundtables

38.068. AERA Roundtable Session Thursday 2:15 pm; Roundtable Session

38.068-1. Abolitionist Pedagogies for Transforming Education and Society (Table 1). SIG-Critical Educators for Social Justice; Roundtable Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Abolish Prisons, Expand Police?: Pre-Service Teachers and the Prison-Industrial Complex. *Alexandria Hollett, California State University - Northridge*

Education Interrupted: An Explanatory Sequential, Mixed Methods, Multiple Case Study to Explore the Educational and Training Needs of Exonerated Individuals. *Tiffani D. Hurst, Drexel University*

From Referrals to Restoration: Centering Student Voice in Rethinking School Discipline. *Tamara Jones, Duval County Public Schools*

JustAI: Dismantling Harmful Historic Roots of AI through Abolitionist and Fugitive Pedagogies. *Marie K. Heath, Loyola University Maryland; Stephanie Smith Budhai, University of Delaware*

Abolition as Ontological Orientation: Being With and For Young People. *Estefania Rodriguez Sanchez, Stanford University*

Chair: *Mohit P. Mehta, Texas State University*

38.068-2. Critical Inquiries into Identity, Representation, and Power in Education (Table 2). SIG-Critical Educators for Social Justice; Roundtable Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Diversity Unit as Racial Project: Lessons About Identity for One BIPOC First-Grader in Rural Appalachia. *Rachelle Kuehl, Virginia Tech*

The Risk of Rushing Ahead: How Dual Credit Enrollment in California Overlooks Adolescent Development in Immigrant

and First-Gen Students. *Melody May Yin Isabela, Claremont Graduate University*

Understanding Identity and Lived Reality: Expanding Demographic Considerations in Educational Surveys. *Corin Bowen, California State University - Los Angeles; Nicolas Rabb, California State University - Los Angeles; Elizabeth Thompson, California Polytechnic State University - San Luis Obispo; Eva Schoirring, STEMEVAL; Gustavo Menezes, California State University - Los Angeles; Michael Ibrahim, California State University - Los Angeles; Yilin Feng, California State University - Los Angeles; Kenya Mejia, San Francisco State University*

Using Critical Literacy to Combat Artificial Intelligence's Bias in History: The Future of Social Studies. *Lyndsey Aubin Benharris, Stonehill College; Katharine R. Covino-Poutasse, Fitchburg State University; Renee Fratantonio, Fitchburg State University*

Unforgetting History, Imagining Futures: A Comparative Analysis of the 1980s NYS Curriculum of Inclusion and the Recent NYC Black Studies Curriculum. *Lindamichelle Baron, York College - CUNY*

Chair: *Cherise McBride, Stanford University*

38.068-3. Crippling Teacher Education: Unforgetting Histories and Co-Constructing Inclusive Futures (Table 3). SIG-Disability Studies in Education; Roundtable Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Co-constructing Inclusive Praxis with Teachers Candidates. *Carly Beth Christensen, University of British Columbia; Leyton Schnellert, University of British Columbia; Amy Caesar, University of British Columbia; Andrea Kellaway, University of British Columbia; Shelley Moore, University of British Columbia*

Inclusive Literacy Teacher Preparation: A Critical Special Education Analysis of the International Literacy Standards. *Kara G. Hollins, Teachers College, Columbia University; Sarah L. Schlessinger, New York University*

Reimagining Campus Design as Racialized and Ableist Structure: Student Narratives of Spatial Belonging. *Vigor Wei Hon Lam, Colorado State University*

Chair: *Elizabeth Harkins, William Paterson University*

Discussant: *Nisha Acharya Julien, Opportunity Consulting*

38.068-4. Embodied Histories, Collective Futures: Reframing Disability and Education in the Global South (Table 4). SIG-Disability Studies in Education; Roundtable Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

A Global South Intersectional Disability Studies Collective: The Importance of Developing Collective Histories. *David I. Hernandez-Saca, University of Northern Iowa; Suman Rath,*

Montclair State University; Monaliza M Chian, University of Northern Iowa; Taucia Gonzalez, University of Arizona; Vanessa Sissi Lazaro Macamo-Santana, University of Arizona; Andrea Espinoza, University of Arizona; Shariese Katrell-Abdullah, Mercer County Community College

Becoming Disabled: An Ontological and Intersectional Inquiry into Disability, Education, and Embodied Transformation in India. Shradha Babu, University of Alabama; Nirmala Erevelles, University of Alabama

The Education of Refugee Children with Disabilities in the Turkish Context. Sultan Kilinc, Syracuse University; Elif Karsli-Calamak, University of South Carolina

Chairs: Tanushree Sarkar, University of Missouri; Arpita Sarker, University of Iowa

38.068-5. Identity, Belonging and Flourishing Along the Margins (Table 5). SIG-Sociology of Education;

Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Nurturing Al-Nafs: Centering Black and Queer Muslims in a Dialogue on Intersectional Identity Development. Toomi Al-Dhahi, Rutgers University

Toward A Sociology of Educational Flourishing. David K. Diehl, Vanderbilt University

Chair: Jawanza Kalonji Rand, Teachers College, Columbia University

38.068-6. Credentials, Certificates and Assessment in Career and Technical Education & Workplace Learning (Table 6). SIG-Career & Technical Education and Workplace Learning; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Cross-Cutting Skills Assessments in Work-Based Learning. Anthony M. Perry, University of North Dakota; Kevin Read, University of North Dakota; Adam K. Atwell, Old Dominion University

Thresholds of Opportunity: Estimating the Impact of Credential Program Eligibility on Communication and Problem-Solving Skill Development. Anthony Mark Gray, Dunwoody College of Technology; Adam K. Atwell, Old Dominion University

Unlocking the Value of In-Company Learning: Certifiable and Transferable Verifiable Credentials in Vocational Education and In-Company Learning. Tom Adams, KWIC; Marcel Metsaars, Koning Willem I College

Discussant: Jennifer A. Freeman, Texas Tech University

38.068-7. Increasing Practitioner Involvement to Promote Authenticity in Hip Hop Studies (Table 7). SIG-Hip Hop Theories, Praxis & Pedagogies; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;

2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Underutilized and Undervalued: Hip Hop Practitioners in the Academe. Tasha Iglesias, Utah State University

Hip Hop as Canon. Cindy Macias, Stay Arts

Hip Hop Practitioners as Content Experts. Michael Conforti, The Hip Hop Institute of Social Innovation; Emile YX? Jansen

Chair: Michael B. Dando, St. Cloud State University

Discussant: Tasha Iglesias, Utah State University

38.068-8. Mapping New Possibilities with Children's and Young Adult Literature, the Arts, and Read-Alouds (Table 8). SIG-Literature; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

"We Make Geographies:" Critical Cartography and Spatial Storytelling in the Secondary ELA Classroom. Caroline Hamilton-McKenna, University of British Columbia

Using Research-Creation Methodologies to Explore Brazilian Cordel Literature in the Childhood Classroom. Nikki Rotas, Western University

Chair: Kelly K. Wissman, University at Albany - SUNY

38.068-9. Networks and Knowledge: The Power of Philanthropy in Educational Change (Table 9). SIG-Philanthropy and Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Art of Reciprocity: An Indigenized Development Guide. Shandiin Vandervere, Native Americans in Philanthropy

Network Governance in Hong Kong's Education: The Role of Philanthropic Influence. Thomas Siu Ho Yau, University of British Columbia

The Quiet Alchemy of Change. Obed Magny, Magny Leadership

Chair: Laurie Beth Goodman, UMASS Global

38.069. AERA Roundtable Session Thursday 2:15 pm;
Roundtable Session

38.069-1. Division A Graduate Student Dialogic Forum - Table 1 of 3. Division A - Administration; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 2:15-3:45pm

Chair: Benjamin Lebovitz, University of Wisconsin - Madison

38.069-2. Division A Graduate Student Dialogic Forum - Table 2 of 3. Division A - Administration; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 2:15-3:45pm

Chair: *Jennifer Banegas, Pepperdine University*

38.069-3. Division A Graduate Student Dialogic Forum - Table 3 of 3. Division A - Administration; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 2:15-3:45pm

Chair: *Marcia Sun, Oklahoma State University*

38.069-4. The Making of Minds: Pedagogies, Literacy, and Progressions in a Changing Curriculum (Table 4).
Division B - Curriculum Studies; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Challenging the Science of Reading Master Narrative: What History Teaches Us about Curricular Panaceas. *David A. Gamson, Pennsylvania State University*

Elementary Educators' Selection of Instructional Materials and Texts for Literacy Instruction: A Systematic Literature Review. *Rashanna Tice, The University of Texas at San Antonio; Maria G. Leija, University of Texas - San Antonio; Gilberto P. Lara, University of Texas - San Antonio; Samuel DeJulio, University of Texas - San Antonio*

Learning Progressions and Trajectories from STEM to Data Science: A Systematic Review. *Zhen Xu, University of Tennessee; Cody C. Pritchard, University of Tennessee*
Making the Child 'Curious': Historicizing a Psychological Object and Pedagogical Tool. *Christopher M. Kirchgasser, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Chair: *Zhiling Meng Shea, University of Nevada, Las Vegas*

38.069-5. Curriculum, Pedagogy, and Historical Inquiry (Table 5). Division F - Historical Inquiry in Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

From Progressive Innovation to Peer Review Scandal: Rethinking the Rise and Fall of Man: A Course of Study. *Mark Hlavacik, University of North Texas; Anna Yonas, University of Kansas*

Legislating Memory: How the Deep South Has Controlled Collective Remembering Through History Education. *Katelyn Dodd, Independent Scholar*

From Busing to Dramatic Arts: Westminster School District's Assimilationist Practices Towards Vietnamese Immigrant Youth in 1980s California. *Gloria Choi*

Unforgetting Pedagogies: Making Sense of Montessori in Myanmar by Non-State Myanmar Educators Amidst Shifting Sociocultural and Political Landscapes. *Maw Maw Khaing, University of Oxford*

Chair: *Elaysel German, Rutgers University, Camden*

38.069-6. Emerging Directions in Historical Methods (Table 6).
Division F - Historical Inquiry in Education; Roundtable Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Recounting Displacement through Space and Time: An Analysis of a Japanese American Oral History. *Shuihan Yi, Northwestern University*

A Historical Look at Science, Equity, and Reading: The Summary Investigations Relating to Reading. *Catherine F. Compton-Lilly, University of South Carolina; Rebecca L. Rogers, University of Missouri - St. Louis*

The Emotional Politics of Fear in AI-Driven Education: A Historical and Affective Analysis. *Rick J. Voithofer, The Ohio State University*

Reframing the Educational Past: A Digital Microhistory of the Sun Family Letters. *Gongrui Wu, East China Normal University*

Undocumented Stories. *Brenda Ortiz Torres, University of Colorado - Boulder*

Chair: *Matt Kautz, Eastern Michigan University*

38.069-7. Historical Inquiries to Make "the history": Unrevealing History from Visuals in the Cold War era (Table 7). Division F - Historical Inquiry in Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Examining the Making of the Post-WWII Literary Citizen through the Concept of "Regime of Historicity." *Britt-Marie Zeidler, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Historicizing Decoloniality in Higher Education: Roger Buffalohead, AIS, and Indigenous Community Insurgency of Minnesota. *Christopher J. Getowicz, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

How Coloniality Becomes Possible in the Name of Health. *Xue Yin, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Historicizing the Notion of Democratic Citizenship: Revealing Coloniality Through Visuals. *Younsun Choi, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Chair: *Thomas S. Popkewitz, University of Wisconsin - Madison*
Discussants: *Stephen J. Jackson, University of Kansas; Sun Young Lee, Wichita State University*

38.069-8. The Impacts of School Discipline Policies on Students' Sense of Belonging and Mattering (Table 8).
Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

How High School Students Negotiate and Resist Restrictive

Cell Phone Policies. *Morgan Mayer-Jochimsen, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Identifying College Aspirations and Behaviors Among High School Students Who Have Experienced School Discipline Policing. *Collin Perryman, Arizona State University*

It's Supposed to Hurt: Student Experiences of School-Based Corporal Punishment. *Meaghan Mingo, University of Notre Dame*

Restorative Practice Program: Student-Led Discipline in Theory and Practice. *Marisol Badilla, University of Arizona*

The Discourse of Discipline Reform: Media Coverage of Restorative Justice in New York City Schools. *Hilary Lustick, University of Massachusetts - Lowell; Rachel Garver, Montclair State University*

Chair: *Marisol Badilla, University of Arizona*

Discussant: *Collin Perryman, Arizona State University*

38.069-9. Mentoring in International and Graduate Education

(Table 9). SIG-Mentorship and Mentoring Practices; Roundtable Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Toward Academia: Understanding the Structural and Developmental Features of Academic Orientation among Chinese Master's Students. *Yang Yang, Xiamen University*

Hybrid Mentoring with AI: Supporting International STEM Graduate Students in Career Planning. *Chi-Ning Chang, Virginia Commonwealth University; Tzu-Wei Wang, Virginia Commonwealth University; Jared P Grigg, Virginia Commonwealth University; Margaret Gatongi, Virginia Commonwealth University; Lindai Xie, Virginia Commonwealth University; Obed Amoakoh Boateng, Virginia Commonwealth University; Yaoying Xu, Virginia Commonwealth University; John Fife, Virginia Commonwealth University; Nichole Dorton, Virginia Commonwealth University*

Silent Transformations: Gender-Perspective Mentoring Programs in six universities in Chile. *Daniela Véliz Calderón, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile; Francisca Beroíza-Valenzuela, Universidad de las Américas (UDLA), Chile; Ana Luisa Muñoz, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile*

Dissertation Chairs' Intersectional Mentoring Practices for Doctoral Student Persistence. *Kimberly Jamison, University of North Carolina - Wilmington*

Chair: *Tanya DaMommio, Texas State University*

38.069-10. Logics & Learning: Organizational Theory as a Tool for Improvement and Reform (Table 10).

SIG-Organizational Theory; Roundtable Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

How Truancy Compliance Officers Navigate Competing Institutional Logics. *Ryan Anthony La Barrie, Vanderbilt University; Eli Rolfes, Vanderbilt University; Hannah Morris, Vanderbilt University; David K. Diehl, Vanderbilt University; Joanne Golann, Vanderbilt University*

"Now You See Me, Now You Don't": Responses to Teacher Turnover in School-Based Collaborative Networks. *Eva Flavia Martinez Orbeagozo, Harvard University*

Systems Thinking in Action: How Principals Shape Teacher Effectiveness Through Organizational Learning Pathways. *Pascale Sarah Benoliel, Bar-Ilan University; Chen Schechter, Bar-Ilan University; Nadav Nehama, Bar-Ilan University*

Toolkits for Centralization: Logics of School District Takeover. *Simone Fried, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Daniel Dawer, University of Texas at Austin; Sarah L. Woulfin, University of Texas at Austin*

Theorizing Capacity-Building in Educational Improvement as Discourse Displacement and Emergence. *Carlos Sandoval, Clemson University*

Chair: *Maxwell Yurkofsky, Radford University*

38.070. AERA Roundtable Session Thursday 2:15 pm - Gold 1; Roundtable Session

38.070-1. Student Access and Navigating Higher Education Institutions (Table 1).

Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Cyberbonding play used to help African Americans collegians navigate a southern HBCU. *Bryan Hotchkins, Texas Tech University*

Leveraging Employment and Co-enrollment Data to Project the College Navigation of Racially Minoritized Students. *Binh Chi Bui, The University of Texas at El Paso; An Viet Pham, University of North Texas*

The (Not So) Common App: Variations In and Influences on College Application Complexity. *Zyrashae N. Smith-Onyewu, University of Florida; Hope Allchin, University of Florida*

38.070-2. Student motivation and academic achievement

(Table 2). Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Biology Doctoral Students as "Docile Bodies": Unpacking the Subtle Disciplinary Power Within Doctoral Programs. *Noha Ramadan, Utah State University; Lorraine Jessop, Utah State University; David F. Feldon, Utah State University*

How Managing Up Fuels Doctoral Students' Work

Engagement: The Roles of Passion and Motivation. *Yutong Liu, Southeast University; Mingyu Li, Buckinghamshire New University; Xin Zhang, Zhejiang University of Finance & Economics*

Imagining Equitable Futures: Evaluating the Perceived Impact of a Graduate School Access Program on Prospective PhD Students' Skills and Understanding of the Application Process. *Mohammed Ibrahim, Arizona State University; Ashley Coughlin, Arizona State University; Blessing Akinrotimi, Washington State University; Sandra Nabulega, Arizona State University; Ayesha Boyce, Arizona State University*

PhD Students' Research Motivation and Research Agendas: Mediating Effects of Research Engagement. *Li-Fang Zhang, University of Hong Kong; Fei Cao, Nanjing Normal University; Siyao Chen, University of Hong Kong; Mengting Li, Nanjing Normal University; Weiqiao Fan, Shanghai Normal University*

Why Academic Master's Students Forgo PhDs: Trajectories, Psychological Mechanisms, and Structural Factors. *Xin Yi Zhang, East China Normal University; Yawen Xie, East China Normal University; Zhu yinru, East China Normal University*

38.070-3. The Role of the State Policy in Shaping Equity, Access, and Resources (Table 3). Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Does Performance-Based Funding Increase State Appropriations for Public Colleges? *Kelly Ochs Rosinger, Pennsylvania State University; Junghee Choi, University of Oklahoma; Justin C. Ortagus, University of Florida; Robert Kelchen, University of Tennessee; Annie Everett, Pennsylvania State University; Muhammad Kara, Pennsylvania State University*

Racial Equity in State Funding for Community Colleges. *Elizabeth Aritonang, UT Austin; Denisa Gandara, University of Texas at Austin*

State-Level Postsecondary Policy as Arbiter of Access: A Longitudinal Analysis of Advancing and Blocking Equity. *Ethan W. Ris, University of Nevada - Reno; Erika A. Bullock, Stanford University*

A Critical Document Analysis of Financial Aid Discourse in California Community College Student Equity Plans. *Edwina Williams, MiraCosta College*

38.070-4. Teaching with AI: Identities, Challenges, and Burnout (Table 4). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Mapping Teacher Motivations for Generative AI Integration: A Q Methodology Study of Early Adopters in China. *Min Lin, Shenzhen University; Guoyu Song, Beijing Normal University*

Exploring EFL After-school Teachers' Identity Reconstruction and Emotion in the Context of AI: A Self-determination Theory Perspective. *Chang Liu, University of Rochester; Zhuoyu Yang, The George Washington University*

Figured Worlds, Class Hegemony, School Rituals, and AI: Ethnographic and Ethical Perspectives on Identity, Harm, and Humanizing Pedagogy in Education. *Chelsia Shanen Panekanan, Texas State University*

Secondary School Teachers' Narratives on AI's Impact in Everyday Teaching. *Carrie Holmberg, San José State University; Brent Duckor, San José State University*

The Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Teacher Burnout - A Systematic Literature Review. *Jingjing Yu, University at Albany - SUNY; Peter Shea, University at Albany - SUNY*

Chair: *Chang Liu, University of Rochester*
Discussant: *Abdul-Qadir D. Islam, Teachers College, Columbia University*

38.070-5. Navigating Practicum in Preservice Education: Ethics, Partnerships, and Culturally Responsive Problem-Solving (Table 5). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Ethical Dilemmas of Chinese Pre-service Teachers During Practicum: A Perspective of Legitimate Peripheral Participation. *MENGFEI WANG, Beijing Normal University*

Preservice Teachers' Problem Identification and Solution Strategies in Culturally Responsive Sustaining Contexts. *Uwakmfon Goodness Folorunso, Washington State University; Yuliya Ardasheva, Washington State University - Tri Cities; Shenghai Dai, Washington State University*

Crossing Boundaries in Teacher Preparation: A Sociocultural (re)imagination of a Midwest University-School Partnership. *Boris Krichevsky, University of Wisconsin - Eau Claire*

"Growing Together Beyond Extended Time": Collaborative Dynamics in Secondary Pre-Service Teachers' Semester-Long Practicum. *Minsun Sung, Korea Institute for Curriculum and Evaluation; Jonghun Kim, Konkuk University*

Negotiating Professional Knowledge: Teacher-Students' Experiences from Practicum. *Konstantin Kougioumtzis, University of Gothenburg; Heléne Bergentoft, University of Gothenburg*

Chair: *Uwakmfon Goodness Folorunso, Washington State University*

38.070-6. Curriculum in Context: Literacy, Language, and

Place (Table 6). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Lost in Translation: The Gap Between Curriculum Policy and Literacy Practice. *M. Priscilla DeVelder, University of Central Florida; Elsie Lindy Olan, University of Central Florida*

Professional Preparation for Early Childhood Education Teachers to Implement Inclusive Practices in Ga South Municipality. *Isaac Awortwe, University of Texas at Austin; Xin Li, University of Houston; Emily Lamptey, University of Education, Winneba*

Resonant Geographies: Gentrification, Place-Based Education, and Soundscapes of Displacement in Tucson, AZ. *Imelda Guadalupe Cortez, University of Arizona*

Use of High-Quality Children's Literature in Elementary Preservice Preparation and Assignments: Literacy Teacher Educators' Perceptions. *Wendy L. Gardiner, Pacific Lutheran University; Chelsey Bahlmann Bollinger, James Madison University; Shuling Yang, University of Maryland - Baltimore County; Roya Q. Scales, Western Carolina University; Ann Van Wig, Eastern Washington University; Linda D. Smetana, California State University - East Bay; Catherine M. Kelly, Concordia University - Saint Paul; W. David Scales, Western Carolina University; Marjorie W. Rowe, East Carolina University; Sarah D Reid, Illinois State University; Stephanie M Lemley, Mississippi State University*

Chair: *M. Priscilla DeVelder, University of Central Florida*

38.070-7. Resource Allocation in School Choice (Table 7).

Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

The Problem with Bill Analyses, in Brief: How a Greater Focus on Students Improves Public Policy Discourse. *David S. Knight, University of Washington; Pooya Almasi, University of Washington; Kendall Fujioka, University of Washington*

Examining the Relationship Between School Characteristics and Proficiency Scores in Tennessee's Voucher Program. *Lauren Huddleston, Tennessee Comptroller of the Treasury*

Universal Eligibility, No Accountability: The Evolution of Education Savings Accounts (ESAs) in the United States. *Trevor W. Baisden, Teachers College, Columbia University; Luis A. Huerta, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Reclaiming Education Fraud and Waste: A Conceptual Framework to Locate The True Sources of Resource Leakage and Harm in The U.S. K-12 System. *Amanda Lu, Georgetown Public Policy Institute; James C. Bridgeforth, University of Delaware; Amanda Lauren Pickett, University*

of Delaware

Chair: *Jin Lee, University of Louisiana at Lafayette*

38.070-8. Rigorous Evidence on the Accessibility and Impacts of CTE and Vocational Education (Table 8). Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Losing at the Starting Line? The Long-term Impact of High School Educational Streaming in China. *Xinyi Fan, Peking University; Yang Yao, Shanghai University of Finance and Economics; Ang Sun, Renmin University of China; Xu Jiang, Xiamen University*

Performance Signal, Selection into Technical Education, and Postsecondary Outcomes. *Yerin Yoon, Boston College*

Chair: *Walter G. Ecton, University of Michigan*

38.070-9. The Cost of Movement: Chronic Absenteeism, Mobility, and Educational Futures (Table 9). Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Chronic Absenteeism: A Qualitative Analysis of Causes and Mitigating Factors in West Texas. *Raven Morris, Texas Tech University; Jessica Gottlieb, Texas Tech University*

Free compulsory education Policy and Intergenerational income Mobility of Rural residents. *Bingjie Liu, East China Normal University*

Musical Chairs and Empty Desks: How School Staff Manage Student Mobility and Chronic Absenteeism. *Bridget M. Curry, University of Notre Dame*

Understanding Non-Structural Student Mobility in Georgia: Implications for Academic Achievement, Postsecondary Enrollment, and Labor Market Outcomes. *Kevin Fortner, Georgia State University; Bogyung Kim, Georgia State University; Natalie Pruitt, Georgia State University*

Chair: *Bogyung Kim, Georgia State University*

38.071. AERA Roundtable Session Thursday 2:15 pm - Gold 2;
Roundtable Session

38.071-1. Professional Challenges in Music Education (Table 1). SIG-Music Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

At the Crossroads: Professional Identity of Mid-Career Elementary Music Teachers in China. *xizi zang, Indiana University Jacobs School of Music*

Internationalizing the Instructor: A Case Study of Global Faculty Development and Exchange in Music Education. *Yi*

Long, University of Southern California
Master's Degrees for Music Educators: Demographics and Disparities. *David DeAngelis, Syracuse University; Matthew Robertson, Syracuse University*
Secondary Music Educators' Perceptions of Constraints and Agency. *Olivia Tucker, University of Utah*
The Importance of Music in Schools: The Superintendent's Perspective. *Ryan D. Shaw, Michigan State University; Cara Bernard, University of Connecticut*
Chair: *Oksana Komarenko, Ball State University*

38.071-2. Narratives of Identity, Resistance, and Reflective Practice (Table 2). SIG-Narrative Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

- A K-12 Science Teacher's Journey in Rural Alaska: A Narrative Inquiry on Teacher-Student-Community Relationships. *Archer Harrold, University of Michigan; Safron LeeJana Milne, University of Michigan*
A Teacher's Journey Navigating Cultural Identity, Resistance, and Decolonization Inside and Outside the Classroom. *Chelita N. Borbon Runbeck, Northern Arizona University; Brena Kee, Northern Arizona University*
Exploring Intersectional Identities Across Chronotopes: A Narrative Inquiry into an Asian Migrant Teacher's Lived Experiences. *Seungwoo Hwang, Michigan State University*
Reflecting Beyond Words: Narrative Inquiry Exploring Multimodal Reflection in Teacher Education. *Amy L. Boniface, Maricopa Community Colleges; Cyndi Moore, Maricopa Community Colleges; Meggin Kirk, Maricopa Community Colleges*
"We sort of broke out of that...": Negotiating Time, Space, and Praxis through Critical Literacy. *Wen-Chiang Chen, University of Wisconsin - LaCrosse*
Chair: *Min Wang, SUNY New Paltz*

38.071-3. Access, Identity, and Equity in Technology-Mediated Language Learning (Table 3). SIG-Second Language Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

- Democratizing Immersive Language Learning: Low-Tech Virtual Reality in EFL Classrooms. *Cemil Gökhan Karacan, Beykent University*
From L2 Text-to-L1 Voice: AI Audio for Reading Equity and Inclusion among Multilingual Learners. *Guofang Li, University of British Columbia; Ziwen Mei, University of British Columbia; Chinazam Faith Okeke, University of British Columbia; Henny Yeung, Simon Fraser University*
Gamifying L2 Literacy in Non-Digital Settings. *Fasih Raza, Texas State University; Alishba Asad, Texas State University*

GenAI in SLA: A Historical, Interactionist, and Ethical Integration Review (2016–2026). *shuang yang, Shu De International High School*
Chair: *Jiheha Maddamsetti, Old Dominion University*

38.071-4. Autoethnographies of Multilingualism: Identity, Family, and Critical Language Pedagogy in Transnational Contexts (Table 4). SIG-Second Language Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

- Decolonizing English language teaching through a Translanguaging Lens: A Collaborative Autoethnography. *Hala Salem, The Pennsylvania State University; Ahmad Ali Khalaf Ali, Pennsylvania State University*
Naming Practices and Identity Negotiation of Chinese International Students: A Critical Collaborative Autoethnography. *Xinhang Hermione Hu, University of Maryland; Xiaohan Gang, Syracuse University; Yige Zou, University of Washington*
Raising Multilingual Children: Everyday Language Realities of Transnational Families in the U.S. *Elena Andrei, Cleveland State University; Mihaela Gazioglu, Westfield State University*
Chair: *Shuying Li, University of Nottingham*

38.071-5. Centering Families and Students in Inclusive Education (Table 5). SIG-Special and Inclusive Education Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

- Beyond Placement: Parental Visions of Inclusion in Autism-Specific Early Childhood Classrooms. *Juliet E. Hart Barnett, Arizona State University; Erin Rotheram-Fuller, Arizona State University; Jesse Fleming, Arizona State University*
Do Autistic Youth Agree with Caregivers About their Transition Experiences? Findings from a National Survey. *Leslie Shaw, Cornell University; Katherine Brendli Brown, Cornell University*
Agents of New Knowledge: A Transcendental Phenomenology of BIPOC Mothers Traversing Texas' Special Education. *Alexandrea Melgoza, Southwestern University*
Understanding Filipino Parents' Special Education Participation Through Immigration History and Capital Theory: a Qualitative Study. *Jackielyn Domingo Ruiz, New York University*
Training in Digital Learning Environments for Caregivers of Individuals with Autism: A Systematic Mapping Study. *Ceren Gokmen, Texas Tech University; Merve Basdogan, Texas Tech University; Ibrahim Akdilek, Texas Tech University*

38.071-6. Disrupting Marginalization and Advancing Equity in Special Education (Table 6). SIG-Special and Inclusive Education Research; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

"Us Versus Them:" Public Perception, Structural Stigma, and the Persistence of Special Education Segregation in Urban Schools. *Faith D. Northern, New York University*

Centering Teacher Views: General Educators' Perspectives of Effective Strategies for Student Behavior Support in Inclusive Classrooms. *Meaghan Kristina Chaplin, University of Miami; Wendy Morrison-Cavendish, University of Miami*

"All Behavior is Communication": How Teacher SEL and Lived Experience Shape Inclusive Classroom Practice. *Kristen Smigielski, University at Buffalo - SUNY / CELARAI*

Evidence-Informed Practice in Autistic Education: Lessons from Research-Practice Partnerships. *Mati Zakai-Mashiach, Beit Berl College; Linor Lea Hadar, University of Haifa*

Chair: *Sarah Hurwitz, Indiana University*

38.071-7. Spirituality as human connection (Table 7). SIG-Spirituality & Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Teachers as Wisdom Workers of Love: A Radical Reconceptualization of Teacher Education. *Anna Lytkina, University of Maryland; Yueyue Wang, University of Maryland; Maha Shoaib, University of Maryland; Jing Lin, University of Maryland*

Ancient Wisdom & Its Cultural Relevance: Reimagining Deep Learning Through A Spiritual Paradigm. *Raaghav Pandya, City University of New York*

Pedagogy of Consolation: A Spiritual and Bibliotherapeutic Approach for War-Displaced Populations. *Zehavit Gross, Bar-Ilan University*

Understanding Children's Spirituality: Conceptualizations by Chilean In-service Early Childhood Educators. *Jennifer Mata-McMahon, University of Maryland - Baltimore County; Xixellonje Nebihu, University of Maryland - Baltimore County; Francisco Javier Vargas Herrera, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Valparaíso; Loreto Bernardita Moya Marchant, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Valparaíso*

Chair: *Judy A. Alston, Miami University (OH)*

Discussant: *Vajra M. Watson, University of Redlands*

38.071-8. Strengthening Teacher Capacity for Computer Science Integration (Table 8). SIG-Technology as an Agent of Change in Teaching and Learning; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Shifting Teacher Mindsets: Elementary Teacher Perceptions and the Transformational Power of Computer Science Learning Experiences. *Mike Karlin, California State University - Dominguez Hills; Jacob M Frankel, Indiana University; Ashley Ruiz, California State University - Dominguez Hills; Swati Mehta, California State University - Fresno; Yin-Chan Janet Liao, Georgia State University; Mahya Minaiy, California State University - Dominguez Hills; Conrad Oh-Young, California State University - Dominguez Hills*

Pre-service Teachers' Knowledge and Beliefs towards Computer Science and Artificial Intelligence Integration in K-8 Classrooms. *Joanna K. Garner, Old Dominion University; Grace K Friedenreich, Old Dominion University; Melani A. Loney, Old Dominion University; Lisa Steffian, Old Dominion University; Jennifer Jill Kidd, Old Dominion University; Sarah Hosni, Old Dominion University; William McConnell, Virginia Wesleyan University*

From Consumers to Creators: Teachers' Professional Learning in Developing Educational Software through Vibe Coding. *Hunhui Na, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Casey Keunhee Kim, University of Hawaii - Manoa*

Evolving Practice: A Longitudinal Case Study of Teacher Growth Through a Computer Science Research-Practice Partnership. *Nitasha Mathayas, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Hilary Mead, University of Delaware; Amanda Nolte, University of Delaware; Chrystalla Mouza, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Rosalie Rolon-Dow, University of Delaware; Jeffrey Robert Klein, University of Delaware; Bataul Alkhateeb, University of Delaware; Shehneela Naz, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Lori Pollock, University of Delaware*

Chair: *Anastasia Shikanova, The Ohio State University*

38.071-9. Systematic Reviews on Technology-Enhanced Learning and Educational Practices (Table 9). SIG-

Technology as an Agent of Change in Teaching and Learning; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Technology-Supported Collaborative Learning in Preservice Teacher Education: A Systematic Literature Review. *Lu Xu, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Xiaoqian Bi, University of Denver*

A Systematic Review of Learning Analytics-Supported Feedback Practices in K-12 Education. *Chaeyeon Kim, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Jewoong Moon, University of Alabama; Jieun Lim, Daegu National University of Education*

Chair: *Zilong Pan, Lehigh University*

38.072. AERA Roundtable Session Thursday 2:15 pm - Gold 4;
Roundtable Session

38.072-1. History, Social Studies, and (Critical) Inquiry (Table 1). SIG-Social Studies Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

"Helpful Geniuses": Pre-service Teachers Learning to Enact Critical Inquiries through Rehearsals with Youth. *Andrew J. Schiera, University of Colorado - Boulder; Andrew del Calvo, Rutgers University - New Brunswick; Laura Meitzen, University of Colorado - Boulder; Daniela Harton, University of Colorado - Boulder*

It Happens Here: Teaching the History of Illiberalism in the United States. *Lightning Jay, Binghamton University - SUNY*

Rehumanizing civic education through authentic classroom curriculum. *Ann Marie Ryan, University of Texas - San Antonio; Samantha Leihsing, University of Texas - San Antonio; Heather C Ramirez, University of Texas - San Antonio; David Vela, University of Texas - San Antonio*

Revisiting History's Interpretive Paradox: Engaging Secondary Sources to Reveal Historical Production in Secondary Classrooms. *Liz Harrelson Magill, Baylor University; Michael A. Krecker, Baylor University*

"Unlocking Historical Thinking: Leveraging Library of Congress Digital Archives to Develop Learning Trajectories." *Meghan McGlinn Manfra, North Carolina State University; Lindsey Payne, North Carolina State University*

38.072-2. Authentic Engagement: Culturally Sustaining Approaches to Values-Driven STEM Education (Table 2). Division C - Learning and Instruction; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Cultivating Compassion: A Multiple Case Study of Altruistic Engineering in a Global Project-Based Learning Context. *Liesel Lutz, Baylor University; Morgan R. Castillo, Baylor University; Maryann R. Hebda; Tracey N. Sulak, Baylor University*

Designing for Joy: Positive Learning Experience Design in Tech Education. *Tamara N. Sobomehin, Stanford University*

Personal vs. Professional Authenticity in Cybersecurity and Computing Education. *Daniel T. Hickey, Indiana University; Ronald Kantor, Kantor Consulting*

Computing Where Students Live: A Programmable Sensor-Based Instructional Unit for Local Learning. *Srinjita Bhaduri, University of Colorado - Boulder; Mimi M. Recker, Utah State University; Umar Shehzad, Utah State University*

38.072-3. Critical Perspectives on AI: Ethics, Equity, and Educational Futures (Table 3). SIG-Advanced Technologies for Learning; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Generative AI Disruption in K-12 Education: Balancing Skepticism and Opportunity. *Shruti Mehta, University of Pennsylvania*

Generative AI in African Higher Education: A Systematic Review of Opportunities, Ethical Concerns, and Preparedness. *Olukayode E. Apata, Texas A&M University; Segun Timothy Ajose, University of Kentucky; Peter O Oyewole, Kent State University; Mohammad Taheri, Texas A&M University; Grace Iyinoluwa Olaitan, Mississippi State University; John O. Ajamobe, Texas A&M University; Funmilayo Labake Hunwathan, Ikoga Senior Grammar School, Ikoga-Zebbe, Badagry; Oluwatosin Mercy Ogunwale, University of Ibadan; Taiwo Feyijimi, University of Georgia; Olabisi Olaitan Adebambo, Lead City University, Ibadan, Oyo State Nigeria*

Influence of Political Orientation on Civic Online Reasoning Strategies in an Undergraduate General Education Course. *Riya Anjaria, CUNY Graduate Center; Elizabeth Shiu Che, Graduate Center - CUNY; Christopher Donnan Gravelle, CUNY Graduate Center; Donna Scimeca, College of Staten Island - CUNY; Patricia J. Brooks, Graduate Center - CUNY*

Uncritical, Inconsistent, or Critical? University Students' Beliefs About AI-Generated Knowledge. *Marek Urban, Czech Academy of Sciences; Helena Beranová, Czech Academy of Sciences; Cyril Brom, Charles University; Jiří Lukavský, Institute of Psychology, Czech Academy of Sciences; Filip Děchtěrenko, Charles University; Veronika Hein, Czech Academy of Sciences; Filip Svacha, Charles University; Kamila Urban, Slovak Academy of Sciences*

Unlocking the Power of Prompt Engineering: A Critical Pedagogical Tool in the AI Age. *Yufeng Qian, Louisiana State University*

Chair: *Azmi Azam, University of Arizona*

38.072-4. AI-Enabled Curriculum and Pathways in Computing and Beyond (Table 4). SIG-Design and Technology; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Blockly-AI into Marketing Education: Teaching AI to Non-STEM Students. *Luiz Barboza, Florida International University; Yeonji Jung, Texas A&M University*

Designing Context-Aware Artificial Intelligence Agents for Computer Science Education. *Chih-Pu Dai, Texas A&M University; Azibun Nuder, University of Hawaii - Manoa*

Prior Gaming Experience on Students' Computational Thinking in Digital Game-Based Learning. *Yanjun Pan, Southern Methodist University; Leanne R. Ketterlin-Geller, Southern Methodist University; Ching-Yu Tseng, Southern Methodist University; Lawrence J. Klinkert, Southern Methodist University; Eric C. Larson, Southern Methodist University; Corey Clark, Southern Methodist University*

Chair: *Zhaochen Gu, University of Illinois at Chicago*

38.072-5. Educating for Ethics through Values, Justice, and Care: Insights from AI and Advanced Analyses (Table 5). SIG-Moral Development and Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

From Knowledge to Values: Embedded Values and Ethics Education Pedagogy—An AI-Assisted Meta-Analysis. *Xuechun Wang, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Alan C. K. Cheung, The Chinese University of Hong Kong*

Impacts of University Students' Ethical Ideology on Their Ethical Sensitivity: A Bayesian Moderation Analysis. *Hongwei Yang, University of West Florida; Jin Liu, University of Texas - Arlington; Liu Liu, University of Georgia*

Balancing Care, Justice and Cultural Contexts in the Classroom: A Framework for Resolving Ethical Dilemmas. *Laurie L. Wellner, Touro University; Linda K Cummins, National University*

Chair: *Alan C. K. Cheung, The Chinese University of Hong Kong*

38.072-6. Transformative Training and Instructional Interventions for Equity (Table 6). Division 1 - Education in the Professions; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Bridging Student Challenges and Interventions: A Systematic Review of Civil Engineering Education Literature. *Zihui Jin, Rutgers University - New Brunswick; Dake Zhang, Rutgers University; Meiyin Liu, Rutgers University - New Brunswick*

Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion Training for Practicing Health Professionals: A Scoping Review. *Hyun-Jin Jun, University of Maryland - Baltimore; Violet Kulo, University of Maryland - Baltimore; Amanda K. Burbage, Old Dominion University; Thuha Hoang, Louisiana State University - Health Sciences Center New Orleans; Sarah B. McBrien, University of Nebraska - Medical Center*

Reimagining Healthcare Simulation Training: An equitable model of medical realism. *Ivana Guarrasi, Minnesota State University - Mankato*

Chair: *Abigail W. Konopasky, Dartmouth College*

38.072-7. Arts based educational research and critical

narrative(s) (Table 7). SIG-Arts-Based Educational Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Quilted Selves: Unforgetting Faculty Creative Identity through Narrative and Arts-Based Inquiry. *Sarah N Dunn Phillips, Johns Hopkins University*

Stories of the Borderland: A Critical Narrative and Arts-Based Study with Heritage Spanish-Speaking Educators. *Adriana V Cardenas, New Mexico State University*

Critical Friendship in the Face of Polycrisis: Metaphors of Hope for Reimagining Educational Futures. *Makie Kortjass, University of KwaZulu-Natal; Ntokozo Mkhize Mthembu, University of KwaZulu-Natal*

38.072-8. Arts based educational research and empowerment in/through the arts (Table 8). SIG-Arts-Based Educational Research; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Empowering Migrant Women in Marginalized Communities through Co-Creation: A Generative AI-Supported Participatory Art Education Approach. *Sifan Pan, University of Art and Design Linz*

From Interview Transcript to Poem: Sharing the Process of Poem Creation for a Study about Lactating Teachers in Schools. *Elise Toedt, University of Minnesota*

Mapping Memory, Making Meaning: Journey Mapping, Testimonios, and Pláticas as Decolonial Arts-Based Research with Latine Students. *Estefania Toledo, Humber Polytechnic*

Chair: *Ashley D. Dominguez, University of Arizona*

Discussant: *Qiana Cutts Givens, Mississippi State University*

38.072-9. Mixed Methods Integration: Theory-Driven Joint Displays for Visualizing Equity Policy (Table 9). SIG-Mixed Methods Research; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Educators' Conceptualizations of Equity and Self-Efficacy for Equity-Centered Teaching in the Face of Divisive Concepts Policies. *Rachel Saperstein McClam, Johns Hopkins University; Sarah A Caroleo, Brown University*

Past as Prologue: A Critical Spatial Analysis of Exclusionary Discipline. *Rebecca A. Cruz, Johns Hopkins University; Dian Mawene, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Allison Firestone, San Francisco Unified School District; Mary Cunningham, Johns Hopkins University; Lindy Johnson, Michigan State University*

District Structure as Inclusion Gatekeeping: Examining Perceptions and Enactments of Inclusion in One

Exclusionary District. *Alexandra Shelton, Johns Hopkins University; Katy A Mullins, Johns Hopkins University; Lindi Shepard, Johns Hopkins University; Rachel Saperstein McClam, Johns Hopkins University; Sarah A Caroleo, Brown University; Rebecca A. Cruz, Johns Hopkins University; Irene Ramirez, Johns Hopkins University*

Chair: *John H. Hitchcock, Westat*

Discussant: *Karly Ball Isaacson, Michigan State University*

38.072-10. Measurement and Assessment in Early Childhood

(Table 10). SIG-Early Education and Child Development; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Developing the Everyday Quality Measure: A Transformativist Approach to Measuring Quality in Family Child Care.

Alison Hooper, University of Alabama; Stefanie A. Wind, University of Alabama; Rena Hallam, University of Delaware; Ekaterina Novikova, University of Delaware; Kristin Johnson, University of Alabama; Whitney Wahl, University of Alabama

Effects of the Multi-Tiered System of Support (MTSS)

approach on early academic outcomes: A Meta-Analysis.

Marta Pellegrini, University of Cagliari; Dylan Dachet, University of Mons; Silvia Cau, University of Cagliari; Nicole Murrioni, University of Cagliari; Ariane Baye, University of Liège; Anne-Françoise de Chambrier, Haute école pédagogique du canton de Vaud; Christophe Dierendonck, University of Luxembourg; Annick Fagnant, University of Liège; Patricia Schillings, University of Liège; Mélanie Tinnes-Vigne, University of Luxembourg; Giuliano Vivanet, University of Cagliari

Building Vocabulary in Kindergarten: Promising Preliminary

Evidence from One Emerging Intervention. *Barbara Wasik, Temple University; Annemarie Hindman, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Katy Egan, Temple University*

Assessing psychometric properties of a measure of Hong Kong kindergarten children's science and engineering knowledge.

Xuanyi Wu, Yew Chung College of Early Childhood Education; Brad Chan, Yew Chung College of Early Childhood Education; Esther Chong, Yew Chung College of Early Childhood Education; Ada Lee, Yew Chung College of Early Childhood Education; Ruoyu Wen, Yew Chung College of Early Childhood Education; Delia Ng, Yew Chung College of Early Childhood Education

Examining Effects of Center-Based Preschools and Family

Childcare Homes on Pre- Literacy and Pre-Math Development — Using Propensity Score Matching Strategy.

QIFAN Zhang, University of California - Berkeley

Chair: *Annemarie Hindman, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*

38.073. e-Lightning Ed-Talk Session 8 - Stage 1. AERA e-

Lightning Ed-Talks; AERA Ed Talk

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Exhibit Hall A - Stage 1; 2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

An Exploratory Study of Interest-Boredom Detection Using Facial Action Units during Interactive Reading (Stage 1, 2:20 PM). *Qiyuan Zheng, University of Toronto - OISE; Jiaju Huang, University of Toronto - OISE; Earl Woodruff, University of Toronto - OISE; Suzanne E. Hidi, University of Toronto*

Seeing the Source, Trusting the Source: What Helps Children Navigate Conflicting Texts? (Stage 1, 2:29 PM). *Haolan Wang, Beijing Normal University; Panayiota Kendeou, University of Minnesota; Xinchun Wu, Beijing Normal University; Jason Braasch, Georgia State University; Yi Zhao, Beijing Normal University; Hongjun Chen, Beijing Normal University*

Elementary Teachers' Emotional Landscape: Insights Beyond Existing Literature (Stage 1, 2:38 PM). *Dionne Cross Francis, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Boran Yu, University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill; Yijia Chen, University of Arizona; Lijie Liu, University of Arizona; Ji Y. Hong, University of Arizona*

Resilience Strategies among Black Male Students in the U.S. Education System. A systematic review (Stage 1, 2:47 PM).

Malachi Okechi Chukwu, Washington State University; Olusola Olalekan Adesope, Washington State University

Supporting Black Students in California Community Colleges During The Era Of AB 705 Legislative Reform (Stage 1,

2:56 PM). *Julia Camille Ransom, Research for Action; Kri Burkander, Research for Action; Taylor Stenley, Research for Action*

Mechanisms of Adaptivity in ALTs to Foster SRL in K-12

Education: A Systematic Literature Review (Stage 1, 3:05 PM). *Ismail Souiri, University of Bern; Mathias Mejez,*

Fachhochschule Nordwestschweiz

Moderating Impact of Gender on Personality and Self-

Regulated Learning with ChatGPT (Stage 1, 3:14 PM). *Yuk*

Mui Elly Heung, The Chinese University of Hong Kong;

Xiaojing Weng, The Education University of Hong Kong;

Thomas K.F. Chiu, The Chinese University of Hong Kong

Understanding the Effects of Simple Analogies on

Comprehension and Metacomprehension in Geoscience

(Stage 1, 3:23 PM). *Allison J. Jaeger, Mississippi State*

University; Micahel Poe, Mississippi State University;

Thomas Daniel Griffin, University of Illinois at Chicago;

Jennifer Wiley, University of Illinois at Chicago; Lena

Hildenbrand, University of Illinois at Chicago; Nicole D

LaDue, Northern Illinois University

Validating 'E' in STEM: How Engineering Fosters Self-

Regulation and 21C Skills in Korean High Schools (Stage 1,

3:32 PM). *Woongbin Park, Purdue University; Hyeree Cho,*

Purdue University; Huiy Lim, Seoul metropolitan office of

education; Yunjin Lim, Chinju National University of

Education; Hyunuk Park, Purdue University; Jiwon Kim,

38.074. Ways of organizing learning in everyday settings: LOPI in Indigenous practices, values, and community collaboration. Affiliated Groups; Structured Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 515A;
2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Shaping spaces of relationality: Improvised music as a context for examining the heterogeneity of LOPI. *Ananda M. Marin, University of California - Los Angeles; Lindsay E. Lindberg, University of California - Los Angeles; Shivani Dave, University of California - Los Angeles*

Maintaining Group Harmony at 'Tinderbox Moments' — LOPI and Cherokee Community Values. *Andrew Dayton, University of Southern California; Barbara Rogoff, University of California - Santa Cruz*

Learning from the Environment: Children's Participation and LOPI in Amazonia. *Camilla Morelli, University of Bristol*
Tsotsil Children's Knowledge of Medicinal Plants: Experiential Narratives and Care in LOPI Ecologies. *Lourdes de Leon, Centro de Investigaciones y Estudios Superiores en Antropología Social*

Preferences in Early Child-Rearing: A Longitudinal Intercultural Study from Chile. *Marjorie Murray, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile; Matías Deneken, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile; Gabriela Piña, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile*

LOPI in The Design of Community-Based Programs: A Case Study of Agroecology Promotion in Guatemala. *Michael Bakal, University of California, Santa Cruz*

Learning by Observing and Pitching In among Indigenous Children in the Chittagong Hill Tracts. *Maung Ting Nyeu, University of California, Santa Barbara*

Niñas y Niños Acomedidos and Culturally Sustaining Pedagogy in Early Childhood Classrooms. *Kiyomi Sanchez-Suzuki Colegrove, Texas State University; Molly E. McManus, San Francisco State University; Jennifer Keys Adair, The University of Texas at Austin*

Children's Stake in Decision Making About Out-of-School Activities in Guatemalan Maya Families. *Pablo Chavajay, University of New Hampshire; Cathy Angelillo, University of New Hampshire*

Chairs: *Andrew D Coppens, University of New Hampshire; Barbara Rogoff, University of California - Santa Cruz; Lucía Alcalá, California State University - Fullerton*

Discussant: *Kris D. Gutiérrez, University of California - Berkeley*

Uncategorized Sessions

38.075. AERA Research in Progress Roundtable Session Two.
AERA Sessions; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;

38.075. Research-in-Progress RT002 (Thursday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Comparing Metaheuristic Algorithms for Structural Equation Modeling Sensitivity Analysis. *Xinyu Liu, University of Minnesota; Katerina M. Marcoulides, University of Minnesota*

Correlation Reporting in Multilevel Analyses: A Practical Guide and Review of Practices. *Xue Han, The Ohio State University; Minjung Kim, The Ohio State University*

Psychometric Evaluation of Three New Student Agency Scales. *Nicholas Balisciano, Harvard University*

Scalable Skill Tracing Using Cognitive Diagnosis Model With Covariates. *Scarlett Escudero, University of Minnesota; Wenchao Ma, University of Minnesota; Nidhi Kohli, University of Minnesota*

Chair: *Jerome V. D'Agostino, The Ohio State University*

38.075. Research-in-Progress RT007 (Thursday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Emerging Women Educational Leaders in Ghana: Preliminary Insights on Career Pathways and Professional Networks. *Ruth Boamah-Agyekum, Michigan State University*

"I Hire for Heart": The Administrator as an Ecological Keystone for Rural STEM Teacher Retention. *Emmanuel Dwamena, University of Connecticut*

Impact of Leadership Style on Student Achievement of K-12 Students. *iqra shahbaz, University of Colorado - Colorado Springs*

Chair: *Linda C. Tillman, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*

38.075. Research-in-Progress RT010 (Thursday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Contrasting How Student Perceives on Human and AI scaffolding in Career Advising. *Yanni Chen, Harvard University*

Topic: Addressing Behavioral Issues through Digital Dependence and Screen Time Impact in American Children Aged 0-6. *Esnart Mfune, University of Cincinnati*

Smartphone Addiction and Academic Achievement: An Educational Impact Study of High School Students. *Erika L. Weber, Lewis & Clark College*

Chair: *Christopher J. Dede, Harvard University*

38.075. Research-in-Progress RT014 (Thursday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Conceptualizations of Gifted Education Programming Among Families of English Learners. *Alejandra Salazar Salame, George Mason University*

High Aptitude, Mixed Signals: College Pathways of Twice-Exceptional Students. *Ashley Rieske, University of Arkansas at Fayetteville*

Chair: *Linda Reddy, Rutgers University*

38.075. Research-in-Progress RT024 (Thursday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Advancing the construct of assessment literacy: A key variable in interdisciplinary research on student well-being. *Karin Portmann, St. Gallen University of Teacher Education; Anna-Lena Ullrich, St. Gallen University of Teacher Education; Robbert J. Smit, St. Gallen University of Teacher Education*

Centering Black Joy and the Pursuit of Purpose: A Restorative Justice Response to the Disproportionate Channeling of Black Youth through the School-to-Prison Pipeline. *Elle Butler, Howard University*

Culture and Growth Mindset: Exploring the Mindset x Context Theory in Korean and American Students. *Megan Tansey, San Francisco State University*

“I expect a lot of things of myself”: A study on the coping practices of housing insecure students attending an accelerated school of choice. *Shanté Elliott, Northwestern University*

Chair: *Amy Stuart Wells, Bank Street College of Education*

38.075. Research-in-Progress RT025 (Thursday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Early-Career Teachers at the Intersection of Emotional Labor and Political Polarization. *Yuanyuan Huang, University of Pennsylvania*

Emotion and Obligation: The Decision-Making of Justice-Centered Early Career Educators in Independent Schools. *Stella K Beale, University of Pennsylvania*

Intersecting Identities in Social Justice Education: A Critical Discourse Analysis. *Franny Perez Ramirez, West Virginia University*

Teachers' Perceptions of their Student's Needs in Kenya. *Maya Anne Cowan, San Francisco State University*

Justice-Centered Media Pedagogies: Early-Career Teachers' Learning and Pedagogical Development. *Mila Re, University of California - Santa Cruz*

Chair: *Janet L. Miller, Teachers College, Columbia University*

38.075. Research-in-Progress RT030 (Thursday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Investigating the Experiences of Iranian Graduate Students Studying in the United States. *Hannah Ameli, University of Georgia; Kathryn J. Roulston, University of Georgia*

Navigating Belonging: Exploring How Generational Status Shapes Student Experiences in German Universities. *Leonie Starke, Bielefeld University; Sercan Erer, Bielefeld University; Frederick de Moll, Bielefeld University*

Teacher Support Predicts Curiosity, Self-Regulated Learning, and Belonging: Evidence from PISA 2022 (Indonesia). *Asis Wahyudi, Pennsylvania State University*

Chair: *Katherine Schultz, University of Colorado - Boulder*

38.075. Research-in-Progress RT033 (Thursday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Beyond exclusion: An Exploratory Geospatial Analysis of Adult Learners, Community Colleges, & Credentials. *Catalina Vasquez, University of Texas at Austin*

CTE Dual Enrollment Pathway Formation: Latent Class Analysis of Course Taking Patterns in Tennessee, 2015-2024. *Jeffrey J. Tinley, Roane State*

Exploring the Experiences of Student Fathers of Color at California Community Colleges. *Ana Fernandez, El Camino College*

In Between and Unseen: Examining the Experiences of Multiracial Community College Students. *Marci Matsushita-Sanchez, California State University, Office of the Chancellor*

Investigating the Role of Financial Support on Student Academic Performance at Community Colleges. *Jiaying Xu, University of Texas at Austin*

Chair: *Kristina L. Zeiser, American Institutes for Research*

38.075. Research-in-Progress RT036 (Thursday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Exploring the Experiences of Late Age on Arrival Multilingual Learners in Postsecondary Education. *Dani Ecklund, University of Central Florida*

Stakeholder Engagement in Evaluation Frameworks for First-

Generation College Student Programs. *Nadia Sahila, University of Massachusetts - Lowell*

Latinx U.S. Citizens from Mixed-Status Families in Higher Education. *Iris Alexcia Vanegas, University of Denver*
Chair: *Edmund T. Hamann, University of Nebraska - Lincoln*

38.075. Research-in-Progress RT037 (Thursday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Gamification in Higher Education: The Impact of Bonus Points on Student Motivation. *Kathleen Julian Dang, University of North Texas*

Navigating Histories and Futures: Global South International Students at Predominantly White Southeastern U.S. Institutions. *Hissah Alzahrani, University of North Carolina - Wilmington*

Shifting Narratives in North-South Higher Education Partnerships: Case Study of CARP. *Elham Chelabi, The University of Arizona*

Chair: *Carol Camp Yeakey, Washington University in St. Louis*

38.075. Research-in-Progress RT039 (Thursday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

A Phenomenological Analysis of Science Teacher Sensemaking around Culturally Responsive-Sustaining Curriculum.

Candyce Johnson, Teachers College, Columbia University

Black Women Science Teachers Technology Integration to Support Culturally Responsive Teaching in Secondary Science Education. *Ashley Thomas, Kennesaw State University; Tiffany Anne Roman, Kennesaw State University*

Sin Fronteras: Urban High School Neplanteros Making Sense of Ecological Borderlands. *Victor Baldemar Leos, University of Colorado - Boulder*

Teaching at the Intersection: STEAM, Culturally Sustaining Pedagogies, and Community Engagement. *Leandro Holanda Fernandes de Lima, University of California - Los Angeles*

Teaching Through A Cultural Lens: A practitioner's Self-Study In The Science Classroom. *Michelle R. Estrada-Quezada*

Virtual Reality and Student Engagement: A Constructivist Approach to Geometry Instruction. *Mallory Brewer, Valdosta State University*

Chair: *Vincent D. Willis, University of Alabama*

38.075. Research-in-Progress RT057 (Thursday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Students' Perceived Purposes of Higher Education: A

Transnational Perspective. *Mianmian Fei, The Ohio State University*

Using Identity-Based Motivation to Examine Engineering Master's Students' Enrollment Decisions And Persistence. *Shuyu Wang, The Ohio State University*

What Are the Perceptions of Immigrant Women in Idaho When Pursuing an Advanced Degree? *Andrea Dayne Soleta Schmutz, University of Idaho*

Chair: *Gregory J. Kelly, University of Massachusetts - Amherst*

38.075. Research-in-Progress RT064 (Thursday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Exploring General Education Teachers' Perceptions and Implementation of Inclusive Education in Liberia. *Lydia K Mallah, Florida International University*

Teachers' Perceptions on Sustainability-Oriented Physical Education: A Comparative Study of Korea and the United States. *Jongho Lee, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Euichang Choi, Seoul National University; Kevin Andrew Richards, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Why Teachers Continue to Struggle with Funds of Knowledge Despite Its Promise: A Comparative Study of Bangladesh and the United States. *Evana Nusrat Dooty, West Virginia University*

Chair: *Judith L. Green, University of California - Santa Barbara*

38.075. Research-in-Progress RT070 (Thursday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Baseline Insights into a Word Study Spelling Program's Effectiveness: Research in Progress. *Robin Miranda, MTSU; Caitlin Deckard, University of Texas at Austin*

Nested Narratives: A Mixed-Method Case Study of Reading Self-Efficacy in Fourth Grade. *Amanda Vesner, The Ohio State University*

Parent Perceptions of Books in Schools. *Lisa Redding, University of North Texas*

Chair: *Joyce L. Epstein, Johns Hopkins University*

38.075. Research-in-Progress RT075 (Thursday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
2:15-3:45pm

Participants:

Cultivating Inclusion: Redesigning Hawai'i Community College Early Childhood Programs. *Lilian Bautista Rebamonte-Smith, University of Hawaii*

From Compliance to Growth: Reframing Teacher Evaluation

For Sustainable Professional Learning. *Allen Baugh, District of Columbia Public Schools; Dylan Ravdin, American University and Bronx Charter School for the Arts*
Global Linguistic Justice Framework for Teacher Education. *Amelia Quonyelle Rivera, North Carolina State University*
School Selection and Psychological Safety: Lessons from Families with Gender-Diverse Students. *Joe Heisler, Indiana University; Shaun Khurana, University of Florida*
Reimagining Professional Development as a Decolonization Tool. *Alonso Gonzalez, University of California - Los Angeles*

Chair: *Nadia Behizadeh, Georgia State University*

Thursday, April 9th, 3:00 pm

39.010. The Journal of Negro Education UN-AERA: Uninhibited, Unfiltered, Uncensored, Unconventional. Affiliated Groups; Panel Discussion
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 411 (Theatre); 3:00-6:00pm

39.011. ~~zzzzz~~ Cancelled Per Email 3-2-26 Where Kids Live and Learn: Actionable Research on Housing, District Lines, and Early Learning Placement. Affiliated Groups; Panel Discussion
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 511C; 3:00-5:00pm

Thursday, April 9th, 4:15 pm

Governance Meetings and Events

40.001. AERA Ethics Committee: Closed Meeting. AERA Governance; Governance Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 514; 4:15-5:45pm
Chair: *Julie M. Slayton, University of Southern California*

40.002. AERA Scholars of Color in Education Committee: Closed Meeting. AERA Governance; Governance Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 513; 4:15-5:45pm
Chair: *Laura E. Hernandez, Learning Policy Institute*

40.003. AERA SIG Executive Committee Meet-and-Greet for SIG Officers (Invitation Only). AERA Governance; Governance Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Concourse Hall; 4:15-5:45pm
Chair: *Norma A. Guzman, Texas A&M University - Kingsville*

40.004. Educational Evaluation and Policy Analysis: Closed Editorial Board Meeting. AERA Governance; Governance Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 518; 4:15-5:45pm
Chair: *John Neikirk, American Educational Research Association*

Presidential Sessions

40.010. Looking Back, Looking Forward, Imagining Futures: CORIBE's Black Education Research Agenda -- Impacts 20 Years Later. AERA Presidential Session; Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 408A; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

“To Serve the Present Age My Calling to Fulfill”: CORIBE’s Vision and Transformative Research Praxis. *Joyce E. King, Georgia State University*

Culturally Sensitive Research and Evaluation: Advancing an Agenda for Black Education. *Linda C. Tillman, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*

CORIBE’s Influence: Founding the Black Education Research Center and Developing NY City’s Black Studies Curriculum. *Sonya Douglass, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Continuity, Evolution and Application of CORIBE’s Black Education Research Agenda. *Gloria S. Boutte, University of South Carolina*

Black Education’s Implications for non-Black People: A Relational Race Analysis. *Zeus Leonardo, University of California - Berkeley*

Chair: *Gloria J. Ladson-Billings, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Discussant: *Kofi Lomotey, Western Carolina University*

40.011. Nothing About Us Without Us: Attending to Youth Desires for Their Educational Futures. AERA Presidential Session; Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Transforming Teaching, Learning, and Curriculum with Youth. *Limarys Caraballo, Teachers College, Columbia University; Shreya Sunderram, Graduate Center - CUNY; Vaughn W.M. Watson, Michigan State University*

Intergenerational Advocacy and the Arts Within and Beyond Formal School Settings. *Jamila Lyiscott, University of Massachusetts - Amherst; Joanne E. Marciano, Michigan State University; L. Trenton S. Marsh, University of Central*

Florida; Princess Garrett, University of Massachusetts - Amherst; Dana Altshuler, University of Massachusetts - Amherst; QuaNae Golston-Thomas, University of Massachusetts; Thandiwe-Wanjiru Delgado-Kinyatti, Mount Holyoke College

Youth Organizing and Civic Engagement. Nicole Mirra, University of California - Los Angeles; Estrella Torrez, Michigan State University; Dana E. Wright, Mills College at Northeastern University

Chairs: Nicole Mirra, University of California - Los Angeles; Limarys Caraballo, Teachers College, Columbia University; Estrella Torrez, Michigan State University; Jamila Lyiscott, University of Massachusetts - Amherst

Discussant: Michelle Fine, Graduate Center - CUNY

Honorary President Edmund W. Gordon Series

40.012. From Dynamic Pedagogy to Pedagogical Analysis.

AERA Honorary President Edmund W. Gordon Series; Invited Speaker Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 403B;
4:15-5:45pm

Participants: Eleanor Armour-Thomas, Queens College - CUNY; Eric Tucker, The Study Group; Paul A. Cobb, Vanderbilt University; Neal M. Kingston, University of Kansas; Gerunda B. Hughes, Howard University; Edmund W. Gordon, Teachers College, Columbia University; Hefer Bembenuity, Queens College - CUNY

AERA Sessions

40.013. 2026 AERA Distinguished Lecture - Re-memory, Genealogy, and Dreams for the Future.

AERA Sessions; Invited Speaker Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 408B;
4:15-5:45pm

Chair: Maisha T. Winn, Stanford University

Presenter: Bryan McKinley Jones Brayboy, Northwestern University

40.014. Ethnic Studies Education across Tovaangar.

Spotlight on Los Angeles and the Region; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 404AB;
4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Liberation as Political Imperative: Foundations of an Ethnic Studies Education. Edward R. Curammeng, California State University - Dominguez Hills; Tracy Lachica Buenavista, California State University - Northridge; David O. Stovall, University of Illinois at Chicago; JC Lugo, California State University - Northridge

Live and Teach in LA: Ethnic Studies Educator Perspectives on

Pedagogies and Praxis. Yadira Villalobos Mojica, 75th Street Elementary School, Los Angeles Unified School District; Scott Aquilles, Mann UCLA Community School, Los Angeles Unified School District

Clearing the Path: Insights from UCLA Ethnic Studies Teacher Education Pathway. Darlene Lee, University of California - Los Angeles

The Development of a Districtwide Ethnic Studies Education Program in Los Angeles. Ron Espiritu, Hacienda La Puente Unified School District; Christine Sardo-Aska, Hacienda La Puente Unified School District

Trans-Indigenous Education: Anti-colonial Pedagogies and Praxis in Ethnic Studies Education. Kēhaulani Vaughn, University of California - Riverside

Chair: Lauren Arzaga Daus, University of California - Los Angeles

Discussant: Dolores Delgado Bernal, Loyola Marymount University

Committee Sessions

40.015. Division F Fireside Chat: Boundless Education: Historicizing Diaspora, Migration, and Transnational Educational Histories in Times of Anti-colonial Struggle.

Graduate Student Council Cosponsored with Division F - Historical Inquiry in Education; Invited Speaker Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 402A;
4:15-5:45pm

Chairs: Darion A. Wallace, Stanford University; Callie Avondet, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign

Panelists: Bayley J. Marquez, University of Maryland; Derek Taira, University of Hawai'i at Mānoa; Michelle M. Morgan, Missouri State University; Philis Barragan Goétz, Texas A&M University - San Antonio; Eve L. Ewing, University of Chicago

40.016. Joy in a Time of Struggle: Actualizing the "FUTURE" of Social Justice Educational Research.

Social Justice Action Committee; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 309;
4:15-5:45pm

Chair: Terrell R Morton, University of Illinois at Chicago

Participants: Antar A. Tichavakunda, University of California - Santa Barbara; Juan G. Berumen, University of California - Berkeley; Erica Edwards, Eastern Michigan University; Ashley N. Woodson, Black epiSTEMologies; Kareem Edouard, Drexel University

Division Sessions

40.017. Building Equity-Centered Leadership: Readiness, Reflection, and Systemic Support.

Division A -

Administration; Paper Session

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, San Gabriel B; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Changing District Systems to Expand Principal Supervisors' Capacity to Support Equity-Centered Leadership. *Daniella Molle, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Richard R. Halverson, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Kelly Lawler, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Arati Bapat, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Shweta Chandrashekhar, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Emily Nott, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

From Emotional Discomfort to Empathic Connection in Developing Equity Leaders: Learning through Multiple Ways of Being and Knowing. *Taeyeon Kim, University of Nebraska - Lincoln; Hyunjin Choi, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Opportunities for Principal Professional Learning: the Relationship Between Form and Content. *Jason A. Grissom, Vanderbilt University; Morgaen L. Donaldson, University of Connecticut; Jessica G. Rigby, University of Washington*

Practicing Equity-Centered Leadership: School Leader Perceptions of Readiness. *Michelle Palmer-Felton, Shippensburg University of Pennsylvania; Wendy Kubasko, Shippensburg University of Pennsylvania; Tiffany Wright, Millersville University of Pennsylvania*

Preparing "Fierce Advocates" for Racial Equity: Examining Educational Leadership Preparation. *Leslie Ellis, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Chair: *Carla Finkelstein, Towson University*

Discussant: *James Wright, Temple University*

40.018. Bridges and Barriers: Factors Shaping Students'

Resilience and Persistence. Division C - Learning and Instruction Cosponsored with SIG-Motivation in Education; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, San Gabriel C; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Who changes university majors and when? Patterns for first-generation college-going students. *Jeffrey M. DeVries, University of California - Irvine; Nayssan Safavian, University of California - Irvine; Yannan Gao, Eberhard Karls Universität Tübingen; Anna-Lena Dicke, University of California - Irvine; Sirui Wan, University of Mississippi; Luise von Keyserlingk, University of Tübingen; Jutta Heckhausen, University of California - Irvine; Jacquelynne S. Eccles, University of California - Irvine*

From Connection to Commitment: How Belonging and Engagement Shape Student Persistence. *Farzaneh Farhadi, Pennsylvania State University; Matthew T. McCrudden, Pennsylvania State University*

Fostering STEM Persistence: Student Responses to an Agentic Orientation Intervention in Biomedical Science. *Cassidy L.*

Martin, University of Southern California; Amanda Vite, University of Southern California; Jeanette Zambrano, California State University - San Bernardino; Carolyn Jess, Texas State University; Lillian Nguyen, University of Michigan; Erika A. Patall, University of Southern California; Carlton J. Fong, Texas State University; Germine Awad, University of Michigan; Keenan Pituch, Arizona State University; Yanyan Zong, University of Southern California; Diane Lee, University of Southern California; Christa Bancroft, University of Southern California; Kristy Daniel, Texas State University - San Marcos; Timothy A. McKay, University of Michigan; Stephen J. Aguilar, University of Southern California; Kevin O'Neal Cokley, University of Michigan

Digital Divides and Educational Resilience: Global Evidence from COVID-19 School Disruptions. *Nirmal Ghimire, University of North Carolina - Wilmington; Kouider Mokhtari, University of Texas - Tyler; Eleni N. Pappamihel, University of North Carolina - Wilmington*

Chair: *Delaram A. Totonchi, University of Virginia*

Discussant: *Tim Urdan, Santa Clara University*

40.019. Bridging the AI Literacy Gap: Systems-Level

Approaches to K-12 CS Education. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Santa Barbara C; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Impact of Computing Education by School Type and County on K12 Students' AI Literacy. *Ally Fu, University of Maryland - University College; Kristina Kramarczuk, University of Maryland*

AI Integration Through CT Pathways: District-Led Strategies for Sustainable K-12 Innovation. *Sharin R. Jacob, Digital Promise Global; Quinn Burke, Digital Promise*

Using Embodied Knowledge to Design, Augment, and Evaluate Machine Learning Models. *Alicia Lane, Vanderbilt University; Atefeh Behboudi, Vanderbilt University; Omer Zahid, Vanderbilt University; Ashley Markatos, Vanderbilt University; Golnaz Arastoopour Irgens, Vanderbilt University*

Curious Coders or Shortcut Seekers? Patterns of AI Use in High School Computer Science Problem-Solving. *Mor Friebron-Yesharim, Holon Institute of Technology; Rinat B. Rosenberg-Kima, Technion Israel Institute of Technology*

Unforgetting Pedagogical Wisdom, Imagining AI Futures: A Systematic Review of AI Literacy in CS Education. *Azibun Nuder, University of Hawaii - Manoa; Chih-Pu Dai, Texas A&M University*

Chair: *Joanna Goode, University of Oregon*

40.020. Division C Shark Tank: Graduate Students Pitch Equity and Inclusion-Focused Research Designs for Funding. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Invited

Speaker Session

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Beaudry B; 4:15-5:45pm

Chairs: *Barbara Thelamour, Swarthmore College; Rebecca Myers, Montclair State University; Micaha Dean Hughes, North Carolina State University; Helenrose Fives, Montclair State University*

Participants: *DeMarcus A Jenkins, University of Pennsylvania; Charlotte A. Agger, Indiana University; Richard Carlos L. Velasco, University of Florida; Allison Zengilowski, Lehigh University*

40.021. Empowerment-Focused Computing in Constructionist Learning Environments. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Structured Poster Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 515B; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

1. Algorithm Auditing as a Method for Teens to Deconstruct Biases in Generative AI TikTok Filters (Poster 1). *Luis Morales-Navarro, University of Pennsylvania; Yasmin B. Kafai, University of Pennsylvania; Lauren Vogelstein, Teachers College, Columbia University; Danaë Metaxa, University of Pennsylvania*
2. Intergenerational Learning through an Ecologically-focused Game Design Project Between Youth and Adult Learners (Poster 2). *Clifford H. Lee, Northeastern University; Lyndsay Schaeffer, Northeastern University; Feifei Shen, Northeastern University*
3. A Study of Latinx Youth's Civic Engagement Through Designing Machine Learning Applications (Poster 3). *Santiago Ojeda-Ramirez, University of California - Irvine; Kylie A. Pepler, University of California - Irvine; Eva Durall, University of Oulu*
4. Empowering Students to Harness the Data that Surrounds Them (Poster 4). *David Weintrop, University of Maryland; Rotem Israel-Fishelson, University of Maryland*
5. Intergenerational AI Literacy: Centering Identity, Community, and Creative Futures (Poster 5). *Hawra Rabaan, University of Maryland, College Park; Sheena Erete, University of Maryland*
6. "A Path to Activism": CS Teachers Developing Critical Agency with Algorithmic Systems through Algorithm Auditing (Poster 6). *Daniel J Noh, University of Pennsylvania; Deborah Fields, Utah State University; Yasmin B. Kafai, University of Pennsylvania; Danaë Metaxa, University of Pennsylvania*
7. Objects-to-be-from: Attending to Embodied Ways of Knowing and Being in Creative Computing Learning Design (Poster 7). *Cassandra Scheirer, New York University; Francisco Castro, New York University; Kayla DesPortes, New York University*
8. Centering Maker Voices and Ideas with AI-powered Support (Poster 8). *Blake Danzig, Teachers College, Columbia University; Emmy Semprun, Teachers College, Columbia*

University; J K Voorhis, Teachers College, Columbia University; Nathan Holbert, Teachers College, Columbia University

9. Data is Power: Elevating K-12 Youth as Multidisciplinary Sociotechnical AI Justice Researchers (Poster 9). *Evan Shieh, Young Data Scientists League; Thema Monroe-White, George Mason University*

10. The Role of Near-Peer Mentors in Middle-School Students' Digitally Empowered App Design (Poster 10). *Ashita Bawankule, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; David A. Hopping, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Mike Tissenbaum, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Chairs: *Mike Tissenbaum, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Ashita Bawankule, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Discussant: *Paulo Blikstein, Teachers College, Columbia University*

40.022. Realizing a new vision for wellbeing education: Driving impactful professional learning through research-practice partnerships. Division E - Counseling and Human Development Cosponsored with International Aligned Organizations/Australian Association for Research in Education - AARE; Symposium

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 7; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Understanding the success of whole-school wellbeing education approaches: Building criteria for implementation and sustainability. *Ruth Aston, University of Adelaide*

Using appreciative inquiry to create a new vision for wellbeing: An industry-university partnership. *Mathew White, University of Adelaide*

Informing a thriving future: Understanding teacher readiness to support student mental health and wellbeing. *Laura Dainton Smith, University of Melbourne*

Constructing a multidimensional hierarchical model of wellbeing literacy: Reenvisioning wellbeing education research. *Janet M Clinton, University of Melbourne*

Chair: *Mathew White, University of Adelaide*

Discussant: *Ronnel B. King, Chinese University of Hong Kong*

40.023. Pushing Measurement Forward: Application of Advanced Quantitative Methods. Division I - Education in the Professions; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 3; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Aggregating Workplace-Based Assessment and Entrustable Professional Activity Ratings using Bayesian Inference. *Andrew E. Krumm, University of Michigan*

Evaluating the Validity and Reliability of General Surgery Milestones 2.0: A National Study. *Dandan Chen, Mass*

General Hospital/Harvard Medical School; Jonah Thomas, Massachusetts General Hospital

Predicting General Surgery Resident Competence: Evaluating Accuracy and Fairness of Statistical Learning Methods. *Ting Sun, University of Utah; Stella Yun Kim, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Gabrielle Moore, University of Utah; Brigitte K. Smith, University of Utah*

Predicting Medical Students' Clinical Empathy Development: A Longitudinal Study with Machine Learning and Cluster Analysis. *Haichun Zhou, Peking University; Ziyue Shen, Peking University; Hongbin Wu, Peking University*

Chair: *Ni Bei, The American Board of Anesthesiology*

Discussant: *Irina Grabovsky, National Board of Medical Examiners*

40.024. Access for Whom? Reframing the Discourse on Equity and Opportunity. Division J - Postsecondary Education;

Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Atrium II; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Navigating New Horizons: College Access for Multilingual Learners through Educator Collaboration. *Lei Jiang, University of Kansas*

Bridging Dreams and Access: Family, Community, and Mentorship in Indigenous Ethnic Somali Students' College Access & Persistence. *Lul M. Baba, University of Illinois at Chicago*

College Advising for Undocumented Students in California Title I High Schools. *Tenisha Tevis, Oregon State University; Ashley B. Clayton, Louisiana State University; Erin Doran, University of Texas - El Paso*

Chair: *Cristina Nader, Texas A&M University*

Discussant: *Adrian H. Huerta, University of Southern California*

40.025. Advancing Faculty Diversity, Research, and Mentorship in STEM. Division J - Postsecondary

Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum H; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Beyond Metrics: How Early-Career URM Women in STEM Navigate Tenure, Identity, and Epistemic Exclusion. *Al Dabiri, University of Missouri; Gina Sarabella, Felician College*

Increasing Faculty Racial Diversity in STEM Departments through Transformative Departmental Change. *Gabriel Lé Espiritu, University of California - Los Angeles; Deborah Southern, University of California - Los Angeles*

Latent Profile Analysis of STEM Students' Support Systems: The Unique Role of Faculty Mentoring. *Shuyan Sun, University of Maryland - Baltimore County; Allison M. French, University of Wisconsin - Superior; Gabriela Marie Rivera, University of Maryland - Baltimore County*

Transforming the Lab into a Living Room: Faculty of Color Curating Communal STEM Learning Environments.

Courtney L. Luedke, University of Illinois at Chicago; Angelina Lavinia Grace Ortiz, University of Illinois at Chicago; Moe Ali Azaan, City Colleges of Chicago

Reimagining Faculty Hiring in STEM: Mentoring as Key Metric for Faculty Diversity. *Channel C. McLewis, University of Nebraska - Lincoln; Damani K. White-Lewis, University of Pennsylvania; Ayin Daleth Morales, University of Nebraska - Lincoln; Megan L Vogt-Kostner, University of Nebraska - Lincoln; Mya Felder, University of Nebraska - Lincoln; Amanda Sue La Paz Torres, University of Nebraska - Lincoln*

Chair: *Aya M. Isaac, University at Albany - SUNY*

40.026. Braving and Caving in Combative Terrains: Responding to Anti-DEI Discourse and Legislation.

Division J - Postsecondary Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum I; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Chilling The Development of Critical Consciousness?: The Impact of Anti-DEI Legislation on Engineering Faculty. *Linda DeAngelo, University of Pittsburgh; Milo Lennette Dufresne-MacDonald, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Charlie Diaz, University of Pittsburgh; Christa E. Winkler, Mississippi State University; Blayne D. Stone, University of Pittsburgh*

Cycles of (In)Justice: Applying the Convergence-Divergence-Reclamation Framework to U.S. Federal Racial Equity Policy. *Saran Stewart, University of Connecticut; Franklin A. Tuitt, University of Connecticut; Kelly Schlabach, University of Connecticut; Stephanie L. Simpson, University of Connecticut; Victor Osorio, University of Connecticut; JaQuan Beachem, University of Connecticut; Wiley Tyrone Dawson, University of Connecticut*

Democracy Under Fire: Understanding Diversity Professionals Narratives of Political Polarization, Legislation, and Public Opinion. *Kaleb L. Briscoe, University of Oklahoma*

Victims of the War on DEI: Honoring A Black Male Resource Center. *Quentin Francis, The Ohio State University*

Chair: *Jimmy Aguilar, University of Southern California*

Discussant: *Darin M. L. Stewart, University of Denver*

40.027. Leveraging social capital to transform outcomes.

Division J - Postsecondary Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum G; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Advocates for students: The role of social capital and care in success after a college closure. *Jesse Moya, Siena College; Jenni Suriano, Siena College; Christina C. Pfister, Siena College*

Agency in LSES Student Campus Involvement: A Social

Capital Analysis. *Sarah Ann Harris, Baylor University; Saralyn McKinnon-Crowley, Baylor University; Tiffani Hoot, Baylor University; Hunter Kulesza, Baylor University*
Muslim Student Sense of Belonging: Identity-threatening, Identity-safe, or Social-identity Affirming College Campuses. *Rasha Alkhateeb, University of Maryland; Laura J. Mahalingappa, University of Maryland*
The Influence of Institutional Selectivity on the Social and Cultural Capital of First-Generation College Students. *Maria Jose Melendrez, Stanford University; Cynthia M. Alcantar, Loyola Marymount University; William Perez, Loyola Marymount University; Roberta Espinoza, Claremont University - Pitzer College*

Chair: *Tiffani Hoot, Baylor University*

Discussant: *Saralyn McKinnon-Crowley, Baylor University*

40.028. Teaching and Learning in a Time of Artificial

Intelligence (AI). Division J - Postsecondary Education;

Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum F;
4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

AI for Teaching and Learning in Higher Education: A 2020–2025 Systematic Review. *Xinting Wu, Florida State University; Shouping Hu, Florida State University; Joe O'shea, Florida State University; Ziyue Meng, Florida State University*

College students' collaboration with generative AI: The roles of task complexity and goal orientation. *Ning Ren, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Gary Lam, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Vivian WY LEE, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Judy Lo, The Chinese University of Hong Kong*

Disciplinary Differences in Students' Epistemic Agency in Learning with AI. *Soyoung Lee, Seoul National University; Hyecheon Ju, University of Cambridge; Thi Xuan Phuc Nguyen, Oxford Royale Academy*

Understanding the Role of Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI) in Student Learning: Evidence from Indonesian Higher Education. *Ibrahim -, Monash University; Aziz Awaludin, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Ahmad Ardillah Rahman, University College London - IOE*

Chair: *Shahin Hossain, University of Maryland - Baltimore County*

Discussant: *Md Mamunur Rashid, University of Rochester*

40.029. Considering the Embodied Knowledge of Teacher

Educators. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Symposium

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 9;
4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Embodied Knowledge in Teacher Education: A Collaborative Self-Study of Child Study Assignments. *Jane McIntosh*

Cooper, University of Houston - Clear Lake; Christine Beaudry, Nevada State University; Leslie M. Gauna, University of Houston - Clear Lake

Inquiring about Teaching to Inquire: Teacher Educators

Explore the Knowledge Embodied in Teaching to Inquire.

Frances OC Rust, University of Pennsylvania; Sonia M. Rosen, University of Pennsylvania; Jessica Whitelaw, University of Pennsylvania

Attending to Indigenous Ways of Knowing. *M. Shaun Murphy,*

University of Saskatchewan; Norine Tourangeau, University

of Saskatchewan; Trudy M. Cardinal, University of Alberta;

Megan Marie Tipler, University of Alberta; Charis Auger,

University of Alberta; Patsy Steinhauer, University of

Alberta; Janice Huber, University of Alberta

Uncovering Teacher Educator Knowledge for Teaching

Emergent Bilinguals. *Celina Marie Lay, Brigham Young*

University; Stefinee E. Pinnegar, Brigham Young University

Chair: *Eliza A. Pinnegar, Anchorage School District*

Discussants: *Cheryl J. Craig, Texas A&M University; Lily Orland-Barak, University of Haifa*

40.030. Emotion, Belief, and Relational Elements of Teaching and Teacher Preparation. Division K - Teaching and

Teacher Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 8;
4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Benevolent Heart, Ritualized Conduct: A Qualitative Study on Student Teachers' Emotional Labor in Teaching Practicum in China. *Yuqing Liu, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Jiawei Zhang, Soochow University*

Cases as a Tool to Surface and Develop Pre-Service Teachers' Ideas About Culturally Grounded Pedagogy. *Tracy Dobie, University of Utah; Liza Romina Escobar, University of Utah; Bailey N. Ondricek, University of Utah; Lynne Zummo, University of Utah; Lauren Barth-Cohen, University of Utah; Connor Warner, University of Utah; Angela Warnock, University of Utah*

Fostering Instructionally Focused Mentorship: Designing and Testing Mentoring Conversation Cards. *Kavita Kapadia Matsko, Northwestern University; Eun Kyung Ko, National Louis University; Lisa Mozer, National Louis University*

Social Justice Teaching Beliefs and Clinical Experiences of Preservice Teachers for Equity-Oriented Teaching. *Afaq Ahmed, Texas A&M University; Hamza Benzina, Texas A&M University; Andrew Kwok, Texas A&M University*

Evaluating Program Alignment Effects on Teacher Emotional Exhaustion: Machine Learning Versus Conventional Parametric Mediation Models. *Jean Baptiste Habarurema, University of Cincinnati; Benjamin Kelcey, University of Cincinnati; Amota Ataneka, University of Cincinnati; Leigh McLean, University of Delaware; Peter A. Youngs, University of Virginia*

Chair: *Christina Lincoln-Moore, Alabama A&M University*
Discussant: *Danielle Igra, Brandeis University*

40.031. Stories That Shape Us: Educators Weaving Culture, Identity, and Belonging. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 6;
4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

- Becoming a Black Educator: Identity, Place, Space, and Belonging. *Natacha Ndabahaganye Jones, University of North Texas; Zutella Holmes, University of North Texas*
- Beyond the Classroom: Using Narrative Inquiry to Understand Educator Implementation of Culturally Sustaining Practices. *Jordana Simmons Berwise, Rowan University*
- Catalyzing Experiences: Early Childhood Teachers' Stories of Bridging Cultural and Linguistic Divides. *Erin E. Flynn, University of Michigan*
- Unbraiding the Past, Weaving the Future: Hair, Heritage, and Educational Belonging. *Beverly Teer, Retired Educator; Tameko Wilson, Educator; Quinci Bone't Teer, Cleveland State University*

Chair: *Erin E. Flynn, University of Michigan*

40.032. Teacher Education from a Global Perspective: Learning from Home and Abroad. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 1;
4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

- Addressing the Shortage: Strategies for Expanding Asian Language Bilingual Teacher Education in Dual Language Programs. *Natalie A. Tran, California State University - Fullerton; Nirmla Griarte Flores, California State Polytechnic University - Pomona; Cindy Li, California State University - Los Angeles; Eduardo Rafael Munoz-Munoz, San José State University; Linda Pham, California State University - Fullerton; Vicky C. Xiong-Lor, California State University - Fresno; Minhye Son, California State University - Dominguez Hills; Fernando Rodriguez-Valls, California State University - Fullerton*
- Induction and Mentoring on Early-Career Teachers' Collaboration: Insights from the U.S. TALIS 2018. *Shaoan Zhang, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Qingmin Shi, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Jinkun Shen, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*
- Novice Teacher Induction and Student Science Achievement: Insights from Three PISA 2022 High-Performing Countries. *Xinyi Mao, University of Central Florida; Su Gao, University of Central Florida; Marjorie Ceballos, University of Central Florida*
- Re-imagining Credentialing: Equity and Advocacy for Internationally Educated Teachers in Canada. *Ayodeji Tolulope Osiname, University of Saskatchewan*

Technological, Pedagogical, and Content Knowledge as Predictors of Tutors' Turnover Intention in Ghana. *Philip Nartey, Holy Child College of Education; Ebenezer Takyi-Wadieh, Ohio University; Felix Asante Larbi, Ada College of Education; Bridget Esther Wayoe, Holy Child College of Education; Priscila Dufie, University of Cape Coast; Enoch Tsey, Ohio University; Cletus Owusu Yeboah, Ohio University*

Chair: *Ya-Fang Cheng, Western Oregon University*

Discussant: *Richard C. Miller, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*

40.033. Transformative Designs for Equity: Teacher Education Pathways Across Communities and Contexts. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 2;
4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

- Access to Empowerment: Supporting Persistence and Belonging in a Program for Future Teachers of Color. *Issam Hafez Abi-el-Mona, Rowan University; Marjorie E. Madden, Rowan University; Gaëtane Jean-Marie, Rowan University; Cory Elijah Dixon, Rowan University; Cori Meredith Brown, Rowan University; Stacey E. Leftwich, Rowan University*
- Co-Designing Care: Transforming Learning Spaces to Center Student Voices. *Gavin Tierney, California State University - Fullerton; Paul S Sutton, Pacific Lutheran University; Rebecca Smith, University of Portland*
- Teacher Preparation for Culturally Relevant Education: A Research Synthesis. *Naheed Abdulrahim, University of Nebraska at Kearney; Michael John Oroasco, University of Kansas; Shahlo Mamedova, University of Kansas*
- Transformative Practices in Rural Education: Leveraging Culturally Responsive Multi-Tiered Systems of Support to Reduce Disproportionality. *Nicole Anthony, Coppin State University; Jale Aldemir, Coppin State University; Mary Granda, Harford County Public Schools; Anastasia Roddy, Coppin State University; Tameka Porter, Towson University*

Chair: *Elizabeth W. Stackhouse, University of Houston - Downtown*

Discussant: *Jessica N. Hiltabidel, George Mason University*

40.034. Opportunity and Outcomes in School Choice Contexts. Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 10; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

- School Choice and Student Sorting: Early Evidence from Florida's Universal Voucher Expansion. *Bingxin Cao, University of Florida*
- Catholic School Choice in a Midwestern City: Serving the Poor and Vulnerable. *Eric A. O'Brien, St. Joseph Catholic School; Michael D. Toland, University of Toledo; David Dueber, University of Toledo*

Charter Saturation and Educational Displacement: Unpacking the Impact on a Suburban Public School System. *Marilyn M. DePietto, Hofstra University; Amy Catalano, Hofstra University*

Student Loans and Intergenerational Educational Mobility: Evidence from China. *Manru Wang, Peking University; Sen Zhou, Peking University*

Chair: *Matthew S. McCluskey, University of Vermont*

Discussant: *Matthew S. McCluskey, University of Vermont*

SIG Sessions

40.035. Struggling Through Together: AAPI and Asian Diaspora Leadership Perspectives. SIG-Asian Americans and Pacific Islanders in Education and Research; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 506;
4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Dragon Lady or Lotus Flower: Counterstories of Resistance of Women Leaders of the Asian Diaspora. *Jessica Wei Huang, University of San Diego; Jenn Thuan Nguyen, University of Washington - Seattle*

Kapwaan Conceptual Framework: Towards a Filipino-centered Epistemology in Educational Leadership. *Virgilio Caruz, Milpitas Unified School District*

Love is a Well of Resistance - Lessons from the Asian Diaspora. *Paul Koh, Towson University*

Leading without a Title: A Vietnamese-American Woman's Counterstory on Resistance in K-20 Public Schools. *Ruby Pham-Stuart, University of Houston*

Chair: *Paul Koh, Towson University*

Discussant: *Jia Liang, Kansas State University*

40.036. Special Topics in Career and Technical Education & Workplace Learning. SIG-Career & Technical Education and Workplace Learning; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Plaza II;
4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Rethinking Graduate Employability in Undergraduate Vocational Education: A Quantitative Validation of the Graduate Capital Model. *Jia Li, The Education University of Hong Kong*

The Early Bird Gets the Worm: The Adverse Impact of Delay Upon Successfully Completing the National Registry EMT Exam on the First Attempt. *Peter G. Kreysa, California State University - Long Beach; Linda K. Martinez, California State University - Long Beach; Henry O'Lawrence, California State University - Long Beach*

Preparing Prospective Counselors for Classroom-Based Career Guidance Using Video Vignettes. *Teresa Giek, University of Mannheim; Juergen Seifried, University of Mannheim;*

Gerald Sailmann, University of Applied Labour Studies
Understanding STEM persistence in vocational education setting: evidence from China's Secondary Vocational Education System. *ZHENG LI, East China Normal University; Shangmou Xu, University of Washington*
Discussant: *Xue Xing, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*

40.037. Innovative Cognitive Approaches to Learning and Assessment. SIG-Cognition and Assessment; Paper Session
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Los Feliz; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Identifying Dynamic Spatial Cognitive Strategy by Eye-Tracking Metrics Using Unsupervised Machine Learning and IRT modeling. *Jujia Li, University of Alabama; Wei Huang, University of Alabama; Kaiwen Man, University of Alabama; Joni M. Lakin, University of Alabama*

College Students' Responses to Feedback from a Diagnostic Assessment of Self-regulated Learning. *Piet Wesling, University at Albany - SUNY; Angela M. Lui, CUNY - School of Professional Studies; Joseph Garofalo, University at Albany - SUNY; Diana Akhmedjanova, National Research University "Higher School of Economics"; Heidi L. Andrade, University at Albany - SUNY; Jason Bryer, City University of New York*

Multimodal Neurophysiological Assessment of Cognitive Load in Children during Math Problem Solving. *Jialing Zeng, Peking University; Renzhe Yu, Teachers College, Columbia University; John B. Black, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Teamwork Cognitive Diagnostic Modeling with Higher-Order Cognitive Interaction between Team Members. *Peida Zhan, Zhejiang Normal University*

Unidimensionality: The Original Sin of Educational Measurement. *Alexander M. Hoffman, AleDev Research*

40.038. Complexity theories in education: Concepts, methods, and challenges. SIG-Complexity Theories in Education; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 502A;
4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Capturing the Complexity of Motivational Climate Through Multidimensional Scaling and Psychological Network Analysis. *Tao Li, Purdue University; Brett D. Jones, Virginia Tech; Saylor Bane, Virginia Tech*

Emergence in social science: Requirements, characteristics, and research challenges. *Stephen D. Whitney, University of Missouri; Wes Bonifay, University of Missouri*

Practice-Based Teacher Education as a Source of Identity Reflection: A Complex Dynamic Systems Case Study. *Joseph Eisman, Purdue University; Andrew J. Schiera, University of Colorado - Boulder*

Reimagining Linear Models: Complex Systems as a Framework

for Understanding Mathematics Teacher Learning. *Kelly A. McKie, University of Delaware; Robin Keturah Anderson, North Carolina State University*

The Evolution of the Use of Complexity in Mixed Methods Research. *Emma P. Bullock, Sam Houston State University; Cheryl-Anne Nadine Poth, University of Alberta*

Chair: *Gwen C. Marchand, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*

Discussant: *Avi Kaplan, Temple University*

40.039. Rooted in Care: Imagining Inclusive and Sustainable Educational Futures for Refugees. SIG-Critical Educators for Social Justice; Symposium

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 301B;
4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Peace Education Program Adaptation: A Sustainable Way for Harmony. *Dilara Özel, University of Glasgow; Zeynep Hatipoglu Sumer, Middle East Technical University*

Accessing Educational Resources and Support: Newcomer Refugee Mothers' Challenges and Resilience during the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Saliha Al, University of Rochester; Mehtap Akay, International Rescue Committee*

Examining Teachers' Efforts to Educate Refugee Students at One Elementary School in Texas. *Nathern S.A. Okilwa, Baylor University; M. Michelle Kelley, Northside Independent School District; Kerry Haupert, North East I.S.D.*

Exploring the Digital Literacies of Refugees from a Funds-of-Knowledge Perspective. *Linda Molin-Karakoc, University College London - IOE*

Engaging the "Between:" Working with Refugee-Background Students and Families amid Complexity. *Ramona M. Fruja, Bucknell University; Kevin C. Roxas, Western Washington University*

Empathy in Action: Nurturing Sustainable Educational Change through Nel Noddings' Ethics of Care. *Alia Hadid, Rhode Island College; Rabia Hos, Southern Connecticut State University; Melissa Hauber-Özer, University of Missouri*

Chairs: *Alia Hadid, Rhode Island College; Melissa Hauber-Özer, University of Missouri; Rabia Hos, Southern Connecticut State University*

Discussant: *Alia Hadid, Rhode Island College*

40.040. Pushing the Curriculum Boundaries in Authoritarian Educational Times. SIG-Critical Issues in Curriculum and Cultural Studies; Paper Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 406AB;
4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Authoritarianism and Post-Truth Epistemologies: Pedagogies of Ignorance and the Production of Political, Cultural, and Biological Bodies. *Erik L. Malewski, Kennesaw State University; Jennifer April Sandlin, Arizona State University; Jake Burdick, Purdue University*

Deconstructing the Legacies of Militarized Discourses: A Comparative Critical Discourse Analysis of Four Antagonistic Ideological Literacy Interventions in Afghanistan from 1978 to 2022. *Nangyalai Attal, University of Massachusetts - Amherst*

Thinking With Surveillance, Thinking With Desire: Diffracting the Use(lessness) of Theory in Education. *Emma Minke McMain, University of Arkansas; Allyson V. Compton, Iona University*

(Re)searching Ethical Vocabularies: Dialogic Encounters with Virtue Ethics in Education. *Paul William Eaton, University of Alabama; Gaston Esteban Bacquet, University of Glasgow*

Too Loud, Too Reckless, Too Ghetto: Fanon, Lamar, and the Racial Unconscious of American Spectacle. *Jake Burdick, Purdue University; Janelle Grant-Ashbaugh, Grand Valley State University*

Chair: *Richard V. Kahn, Antioch University*

Discussant: *Elaysel German, Rutgers University, Camden*

40.041. Responses to Pedagogical Impediments in Unforgetting History. SIG-Critical Peace Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Plaza III;
4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Beyond Contact: An Asymmetrical Struggle for Recognition in a Palestinian-Jewish Dialogue. *Avy Dwight Hemy, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev; Sarab Yunes Abu-Rabia-Queder, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev; Assaf Meshulam, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev*

Teaching in Exile: Embodied Pedagogies of Displaced Academics for Peace and Justice. *Anastasia Lavrenyuk, University of Maryland*

Teaching through tension: Engaging refugee background students' difficult knowledge through critical improvisations. *Thursica Kovinthan Levi, Toronto Metropolitan University; Laxana Paskaran, York University*

Vulnerability as Pedagogy: Norwegian Dialogue Facilitators Navigate Discomfort in Peace Education. *Cindy Yovanov, Drexel University*

Chair: *Adnan Turan, Arizona State University*

40.042. Leading Under Pressure: Scholar-Practitioner Research on Equity-Minded Data Use. SIG-Data-Driven Decision Making in Education; Symposium

InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 7th Floor, Hollywood Ballroom I; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Data Use for Equity, Data Use for Hope: Finding Opportunity in Trying Times. *Stephanie L. Dodman, George Mason University*

Exploring the Ecology of Equity and Data: A Multilevel District Case. *Sarah Jay, Boston Public Schools; Ondrea Johnston, Boston Public Schools; Lindsay Mosca, Boston*

College; Tiffany Ostrander, Vincent Cho, Boston College
Access and Opportunity: Factors Influencing AP Enrollment for Black and Hispanic/Latino Students. *Corey Dwyer, Beacon High School; Elizabeth Leisy Stosich, Fordham University*
Improving problem-solving team activity in an urban elementary school: An improvement science study. *Jamie Henderson, Indiana University; Chad Lochmiller, Indiana University*

Chair: *Vincent Cho, Boston College*

Discussant: *Jo Beth Jimerson, Texas Christian University*

40.043. Beyond Extraction: Islamic Community Practices as Liberatory Research. SIG-Decolonial, Postcolonial, and Anti-Colonial Studies in Education; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 303B;
4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Reciprocal Pedagogies: MusCrit as Methodology for Decolonial Knowledge Relations. *Noor Ali, Northeastern University*

Sacred Circles, Transformative Spaces: Halaqa as a Model for Decolonial Education. *Ambereen Khan-Baker, National Education Association*

Intersecting Literacies and Identities: A Justice-Oriented Framework for Muslim Adolescents. *Fatima Seyma Kizil, Syracuse University*

Decolonizing Wellness: Muslim Women's Faith-Informed Practices of Healing. *Fatima Koura, Northeastern University*

Halaqah as Decolonial-Decolonizing Praxis: Muslim Undergraduate STEM Education and the Promise of MusCrit. *Vivian Zohery, University of Maryland*

The Mokha Majlis Method M3 : A MusCrit-Informed Collaborative Storytelling Gathering. *Carolyn M. Lane, California State University - Bakersfield*

Chair: *Noor Ali, Northeastern University*

Discussant: *Hina Rehman, Rutgers University*

40.044. A Participatory Workshop on Metacognition and Reflective Practice in Design-Based Research. SIG-Design and Technology; Workshop
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Santa Anita A; 4:15-5:45pm

Chair: *Tessa Forshaw, Harvard University*

Presenters: *Eileen McGivney, Northeastern University; Richard Cox Braden, Stanford University*

40.045. Legal Frameworks and Policy Paradigms: Shaping Disability and Access in Education. SIG-Disability Studies in Education; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 511AB;
4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Breach of Duty: Conley v. Calkins and the Literacy Industrial Complex. *Kathleen M. Collins, Pennsylvania State*

University; Maggie Beneke, University of Washington
Constructing, Capturing, and Commodifying Racialized Disability: Historical Throughlines in post-Brown Virginia Pupil Placement Practices. *Jenna Gabriel, Virginia Commonwealth University*

How Two Disability-Inclusive Curriculum State Policies Came to Be: A Narrative Comparative Case Study. *Madeline P. Boehning, Rowan University*

Impact of AB 705 and Transfer-Level Courses on Community College Student Outcomes. *Rachelle Lopez, California State University - Long Beach*

Chair: *Sara Jo Soldovieri, The IDEAL School*

Discussant: *Patience Amadu, University of Colorado - Colorado Springs*

40.046. Computational Playgrounds: Foundations and Futures of AI, Play, and Pedagogy in Early Childhood. SIG-Early Education and Child Development; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Georgia I;
4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Young Children's Perception and Interaction with Intelligent Agents: A Scoping Review. *Grace Yaxin Xing, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Zhuoyun Cai, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Yuya Yamamoto, University at Buffalo - SUNY; X. Christine Wang, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

Preparing Young Children for an AI Future: What Two Decades of CT Research Tell Us. *X. Christine Wang, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Chris Proctor, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Xintian Tu-Shea, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Grace Yaxin Xing, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Zhuoyun Cai, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

An Artificial Tool or Natural Support? Teachers' Utilization of AI in Early Literacy Instruction. *Chenyi Zhang, Georgia State University; Lauren Margulieux, Georgia State University; Nooshin Haddadian, Georgia State University*
Exploring Pathways to Creativity in Early Childhood through AI-Enhanced Musical Play. *Ilene R. Berson, University of South Florida; Michael J. Berson, University of South Florida*

Hong Kong Kindergarten Children's Play with Educational Robotics: Child Engagement and Its Association with Computational Thinking. *Xiaoyi Hu, The Education University of Hong Kong; Weipeng Yang, The Education University of Hong Kong; Hui Li, The Education University of Hong Kong*

Zooming Out: How AI Agents Help Young Children See Interdependence in Ecological Systems. *Xintian Tu-Shea, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

Chairs: *X. Christine Wang, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Xintian Tu-Shea, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

Discussant: *Joshua Adam Danish, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

40.047. Schooling in the Anthropocene: Research Perspectives and Policy Priorities. SIG-Environmental Education;

Symposium

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 401;
4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

- Education and Climate Change: Synthesizing the Evidence to Guide Future Research. *Matthew A. Kraft, Brown University; Grace Falken, University of Washington*
- National Landscape Report. *Natalie Spitzer, University of Texas at Austin; Sarah L. Klevan, Learning Policy Institute; Jennifer A. Bland, Learning Policy Institute*
- The State of Our Schools. *Mary Filardo, 21st Century School Fund*
- Where Do You Go When Home Is Gone?: Teacher Turnover and Migration following Climate Disasters. *Megan K. Rauch Griffard, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Bradley Marianno, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Amanda Hoffman, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*

Chair: *Jennifer A. Bland, Learning Policy Institute*

Discussant: *Jeffrey M. Vincent, University of California - Berkeley*

40.048. Transformation from Within and Outside of Schools: Residency-based preparation for education professionals supporting systemic change. SIG-Experiential Education and Community Engagement: Scholarship and Practice;

Symposium

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Georgia II;
4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

- Critical Foundations: Building a shared understanding and collective practice for justice-oriented education reform. *Sabrina L. Wesley-Nero, Georgetown University*
- Institutional Prerequisites and Obstacles to Building a Program Committed to Educational Transformation. *Douglas S. Reed, Georgetown University*
- Building "Brave Spaces" Toward Anti-racism through Race-alike Affinity Groups. *Kristin Sinclair, Georgetown University*
- Affordances and Challenges of the Residency Model Embedded in the City's Education Landscape. *Mingzhu Deng, Georgetown University*
- Blurring the Boundaries between Teaching and Advocacy: The Capstone as a site of collaborative inquiry. *Kevin Donley, Georgetown University*

Chair: *Sabrina L. Wesley-Nero, Georgetown University*

Discussant: *Alisha Butler, Wesleyan University*

40.049. Technology-enhanced Learning in K-12 STEM

Education. SIG-Instructional Technology; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Santa Anita B; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

- Flowers, Bees, and Gardens: Using Mobile AR to Support

Families' Pollinator Science Learning. *Heather Toomey Zimmerman, Pennsylvania State University; Susan M. Land, Pennsylvania State University; Yanping Xu, Pennsylvania State University; Leqi Li, Pennsylvania State University*

Effectiveness of explicit guidance and practices on abstraction (EGPA): Focusing on computational tasks in a fifth-grade STEM-integrative robotic education program. *Yingxiao Karen Qian, University of South Carolina*

Collaborative Flow with Tangible Coding Toys in Early Elementary. *Camille Lund, Utah State University; Jessica F. Shumway, Utah State University; Jody E. Clarke-Midura, Utah State University; Deborah Silvis, SUNY - College at Cortland; Boram Lee, Utah State University; Anahita Ashineh, Utah State University; Asmaa Yazidi Alaoui, Utah State University*

Exploring the Relation of Prior Experiences and Music Preferences in a Summer Camp on Coding with Music. *Santiago Ospina-Tabares, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Yifan Zhang, Beijing Normal University; Tania Cruz Cordero, Child Helpline International; Chrystalla Mouza, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Lori Pollock, University of Delaware*

Standalone Digital Learning Programs Outperform Traditional Classroom Instruction in PreK-12 Math and Science: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Laura Michaelson, American Institutes for Research; Qi Zhang, American Institutes for Research; Kamal Middlebrook, American Institutes for Research*

Chair: *Bo Pei, University of South Florida*

40.050. Supporting Multilingual Learners' Literacies Through Translingual Practices and Pedagogies. SIG-Language and Social Processes; Symposium

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 501B;
4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Moving Towards Linguistic Justice in Literacy Learning Through Multilingual Literature Partners. *Faythe Beauchemin, Boston College; Lexi Woodward, University of Arkansas*

Translingual, Digital Comic Book Composing: Teacher Instructional Moves in a Multilingual, English-Medium Second-Grade Classroom. *Lindsey W. Rowe, Clemson University*

Designing Equitable Learning Spaces for Immigrant Children Through Transnational and Translanguaging Pedagogies. *Jungmin Kwon, Michigan State University*

From Undergraduate Coursework to Elementary Classroom Instruction: Early Career Teachers Enacting Translanguaging Pedagogies. *Jennifer Anne McCreight, Kent State University; Jackie Ridley, Kent State University*

Examining Diverse Elementary Preservice Teachers' Pedagogical Beliefs through a Translanguaging Lens. *Jessica Somerville-Braun, Skidmore College*

Chairs: *Lindsey W. Rowe, Clemson University; Faythe Beauchemin, Boston College*

Discussants: *Faythe Beauchemin, Boston College; Lindsey W. Rowe, Clemson University*

40.051. Beyond Mere Performance: Educational Equity and Effectiveness in International Large-Scale Assessment Research. SIG-Large-Scale Assessment; Symposium InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Echo Park; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

How reading competence and age of arrival shape educational outcomes. *Lisa Teufele, Technical University of Munich; Clievin Selva, University of Hildesheim*

Multidimensional Goals Matter: How Teachers' Educational Goals Shape Motivational Task Design and Student Motivation. *Pia Todtenhöfer, Technical University of Munich; Anja Schiepe-Tiska, Koblenz University*

Teaching Quality Reduces Socioeconomic Inequalities in Student Achievement - Evidence from PISA 2022. *Tamara Kastorff, Technical University of Munich; Pia Todtenhöfer, Technical University of Munich; Samuel Greiff, University of Luxembourg*

Socioeconomic Disparities and COVID-19 Effects on Student Achievement: Insights from PISA 2018 and 2022. *Maren Müller, Technical University of Munich; Jacqueline Carbajal, Technical University of Munich; Lena Keller, Kiel University (CAU); Tamara Kastorff, Technical University of Munich*

Chair: *Tamara Kastorff, Technical University of Munich*

Discussant: *Bernhard M. Ertl, Universität der Bundeswehr München*

40.052. The Use of Advanced Statistical Methods in the Study of Students and the Teaching Workforce Over Time. SIG-Longitudinal Studies; Paper Session Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 303A; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

From Tool to Crutch: The Longitudinal Impact of AI Dependence on Academic Innovation in Doctoral Training. *Yutong Liu, Southeast University; Jiangtao Han, Xihua University; Entao Ma, Guangzhou University*

Linking School Refusal to Academic Stress and Emotions via Cross-lagged Panel Network Analysis. *NA FU, Beijing Normal University; Xiaochen Xie, The University of North Carolina at Greensboro*

Teacher Retention and Separation in Wyoming: Insights from Survival Analysis and Longitudinal Cohorts. *Bolaji Aderibigbe Akorede, University of Wyoming; Mark A. Perkins, University of Colorado - Colorado Springs*

Chair: *Barbara Schneider, Michigan State University*

Discussant: *Barbara Schneider, Michigan State University*

40.053. Marx, Education, Today. SIG-Marxian Analysis of Society, Schools and Education; Paper Session Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Los Cerritos; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

A Marxian Analysis of Society and The Structure of Schooling: Advancing Critical Realism For Cultivating Humanistic Pedagogies. *Jesus Jaime-Diaz, Colorado State University Pueblo*

Eco-Marxism and Ecopedagogy to Disrupt the Anthropocene: Connections, Conflicts, and Possibilities. *Greg William Misiaszek, Tohoku University*

Martin Carnoy's Marxism: Applying Neo-Marxist Educational Theory to Contemporary Market Reforms. *Mia Fullerton, Reed College*

Naming the capitalist elephant in the room: negative pedagogy. *Raul Olmo Fregoso Bailón, University of Nevada - Reno; Gergana Neycheva Petrova, Universidad de Guanajuato*

Chair: *Phoebe Gilpin, Borough of Manhattan Community College*

Discussant: *David Isaac Backer, Seton Hall University*

40.054. Reimagining Youth Learning and New Spaces for Digital Action. SIG-Media, Culture, and Learning; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum J; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Speculative Mapping of Pressing Civic Issues through a Scaffolded Learning Design. *Matt DeRoo, Florida International University; Gabriela Goitia Vazquez, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Reimagining the Self in Virtual-Physical Third Spaces. *Xuanya Zhou, University of Florida; Huan Gao, University of Memphis*

Challenging and (Re)Positioning African Identity Narratives via Digital Literacies. *Neisha Terry Young, Stony Brook University - SUNY; Angela Ochoa, Stony Brook University - SUNY; Tunazinna Rosa, Stony Brook University - SUNY; Mehwish Hasan, Stony Brook University - SUNY; Christopher Montalbano, Stony Brook University - SUNY*

A Critical Multimodal Content Analysis of Videogames, Policing, and Public Pedagogy. *Earl Aguilera, California State University - East Bay; Joel De Jesus Lovos, University of California - Santa Cruz; Katherine Kafonek, Stockton University*

GenAI-Integrated Digital Storytelling with Teachers of Refugee-Background Youth: Toward Transformative Digital Multimodal Composing. *Amir Michalovich, University of Manitoba; Shawn Porteous, River East Transcona School Division*

Chair: *T. Philip Nichols, Baylor University*

40.055. Learning Through Time: Multigenerational Narratives and Critical Mentoring. SIG-Mentorship and Mentoring

Practices; Workshop

Westin Bonaventure, Level 3, Avalon; 4:15-5:45pm

Chair: *Patricia D. Quijada Cerecer, University of California - Davis*

Participants: *Julie Lopez Figueroa, Sacramento State University; Gloria M. Rodriguez, University of California - Davis; Aida Hurtado, University of California - Santa Barbara; Daniel Gilbert Solorzano, University of California - Los Angeles*

Discussant: *Yanira Madrigal-Garcia, California State University - Sacramento*

40.056. Bridging Moral, Emotional, and Character Education in Diverse Educational Settings. SIG-Moral Development and Education; Paper Session

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Santa Anita C; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Beyond Aptitudes and Occupations: Reconceptualizing Korean Career Education from a Social and Emotional Learning Perspective. *Jonga Lee, Sungkyunkwan University; Saetbyul Kim, The University of Hong Kong*

The Co-development of Children's Prosocial Behaviors and Peer Relationships and Its Relation to Post-Secondary Education Enrollment. *Su Jiang, University of Houston Downtown; Jeffrey Liew, Texas A&M University*

Knowledge and Implementation of a Character Framework in Higher Education. *Luisa Engeldinger, Montclair State University; Anglin Thevaraja, Montclair State University; Alexis Nager, Montclair State University; Elyse L. Postlewaite, Montclair State University; Nicole Sochaczewski, American Institutes for Research; Elaine Les, Montclair State University; Megan K. Hennessy, Arizona State University; Cristy Guleserian, Arizona State University; Miriam Linver, Montclair State University; Jennifer Brown Urban, Montclair State University*

Framing Moral Questions: A Comparative Study of Question Design in Chinese and Japanese Junior Secondary Moral Education Textbooks. *XUAN WU, Shandong University*

40.057. Extending the General Linear Model: From Classical Regression to Bayesian Estimation and Machine Learning. SIG-Multiple Linear Regression: The General Linear Model; Paper Session

InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 6th Floor, Broadway; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Machine Learning in Large-Scale Educational Assessment: A Systematic Review of Methods, Rigor, and Model Performance. *Oluwaseun Peter Farotimi, University of Tennessee; Comfort Happiness Omonkhodion, University of Central Florida; Funke Anuoluwapo Dada, Georgia Southern University; Seun Ajoseh, University of Florida; Debbie L. Hahs-Vaughn, University of Central Florida; Haiyan Bai, University of Central Florida*

An Excel GLM Program for Statistics Classes and Beyond.

Mary G. Lieberman, Florida Atlantic University; Maria D. Vásquez-Colina, Florida Atlantic University; John D. Morris, Florida Atlantic University

Assessing the Performance of Bayesian and Traditional Estimators in Confirmatory Factor Analysis with Sparse Likert-Scale Data. *Jin Liu, University of Texas - Arlington; Liu Liu, University of Georgia; Wei Jiang, University of Texas - Arlington*

Measuring Teacher Agency: A Quantitative Investigation of the Ecological Model. *Christopher Carter, University of Kansas*

Multi-Dimensional Teacher Support and Reading Performance: The Moderating Role of Immigrant Status in the U.S.

Zhicong Song, McGill University; Rongxiu Wu, Harvard University

Chair: *Liu Liu, University of Georgia*

Discussant: *Ergul Demir, Ankara University*

40.058. Elements of Instructional Design in Online Settings.

SIG-Online Teaching and Learning; Paper Session

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Santa Barbara A; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Integrating Learning Analytics into Instructional Design: A Decade of Empirical Evidence in Higher Education. *Seydeh Fatemeh Dadashpour, Purdue University; Fnu Basori, Purdue University; Xiyu Wang, Purdue University; Jennifer C. Richardson, Purdue University; Yukiko Maeda, Purdue University; Yoshiko Goda, Kumamoto University; Masanori Yamada, Kyushu University; Xuewang Geng, Kyushu University*

Supporting Instructional Sense-Making Through Early Engagement Clustering in Online Professional Learning. *Sophia Soomin Lee, University of Florida*

Detecting Teaching Presence in Online Discussions Using Tree-Based Classifiers. *Huan Kuang, Florida State University; Secil Caskurlu, Florida State University; Hui Shi, Florida State University; Kadir Kozan, Florida State University; Seungjie Clarice Han, Florida State University; Sihan Jian, Florida State University; Jaesung Hur, Florida State University*

Online microcredentials' usefulness for promoting elementary teachers' integration of computer science into core content lessons. *Joseph Arthur Brobst, Old Dominion University; Lisa Steffian, Old Dominion University; Melani A. Loney, Old Dominion University; Joanna K. Garner, Old Dominion University; Shan L. Chappell, Old Dominion University*

Chair: *Anna Henshaw Morrison, Clemson University*

40.059. From Funding to Futures: How Philanthropy Constructs Educational Landscapes. SIG-Philanthropy and Education; Paper Session

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Los Feliz; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Mapping the Imprint Foundation-Funded Research in Federal and State Education Policies. *Samantha Jo Shewchuk, University of Delaware; Caitlin Farrell, University of Colorado - Boulder; Elizabeth N. Farley-Ripple, University of Delaware; Lok-Sze Wong, University of North Texas; Joel R. Malin, Miami University (OH); Jennifer Watling Neal, Michigan State University*

Rethinking Philanthropy: A Nexus of Systems Theory and Critical Pedagogy Towards Sustainable Equity for Districts. *Nicole Williams Browning, California State University - East Bay*

The XQ Institute and New Forms of Education Philanthropy. *Brett Gardiner Murphy, Graduate Center - CUNY*

Why They Fundraise: Black Advancement Leaders and Their Commitment to Private HBCUs. *Brandy Rae Jackson, Howard University*

Chair: *Ida Oberman, Alanus University of Arts and Social Sciences*

40.060. “The Witness as Educator” (Book Symposium). SIG-Philosophical Studies in Education; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304B;
4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Participant. *David T. Hansen, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Participant2. *Samantha Deane, University of Notre Dame*

Participant3. *Alexandros Charalampos Nikolaidis, University of Central Florida*

Participant4. *Susan Verducci, San José State University*

Chair: *Ginger Mayhew, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Discussants: *Samantha Deane, University of Notre Dame; Alexandros Charalampos Nikolaidis, University of Central Florida; Susan Verducci, San José State University*

40.061. Rethinking Qualitative Research Methodologies and the Roles of Resistance for Critical Self-Determination. SIG-Qualitative Research; Symposium
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor,
Wilshire Grand Ballroom II; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Anti-colonial Praxis Under Fascism: Experiments in Democratic Learning, Participatory Consciousness and Movement Work. *Ndindi Kitonga, Angeles Workshop School*

Differences, not divisiveness: bridging the binaries of male/female and white/brown while exploring the phenomenon of becoming Muslim. *Dina M. Eletreby, Chapman University*

Inquiry into the social construction of whiteness through my own veil of whiteness. *Veronica E. Bloomfield, Porch Swing Productions*

Chairs: *Mere Berryman, University of Waikato; Suzanne SooHoo, Chapman University*

Discussant: *Christine E. Sleeter, California State University -*

Monterey Bay

40.062. Methodological Considerations for Rasch Measurement Research. SIG-Rasch Measurement; Paper Session
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 6th Floor,
Mission; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Measuring the Stability of Rasch Fit Statistics Using Nonparametric Bootstrapping. *Andrew Krist, University of Alabama; Stefanie A. Wind, University of Alabama*

Exploring the Relationship between Rater Effect Indicators from the Many-Facet Rasch Model and Network Analysis with Incomplete Scoring Designs. *Stefanie A. Wind, University of Alabama; Daniel O. Oyeniran, University of Alabama*

Using Rasch-Based Indices to Detect Careless Responses in Surveys with Missing Data. *Yuan Ge, The College Board; Stefanie A. Wind, University of Alabama; Eli Andrew Jones, University of Memphis; Chia-Lin Tsai, University of Northern Colorado*

Using Simulation to Evaluate Classification Consistency. *Angela Adrienne Walker, Ascend Learning; Kari Hodge, Ascend Learning*

Chair: *Daniel O. Oyeniran, University of Alabama*

40.063. Islamic Studies and Arabic: Integrated Curricular Approaches for Intensive Programs, Faith-Based Education, and Public Schools. SIG-Religion and Education; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 301A;
4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Integrated Islamic Education: Futuring Beyond Bifurcated Learning and Muslim Identity Development in Western Contexts. *Mona M. Abo-Zena, University of Massachusetts - Boston; Aaron Spevack, Brandeis University*

Threads of Meaning: Reclaiming Values-Based Integration for K-12 Curricula. *Ismail Muhammad ibn Ali, Al Fatih Academy*

Chair: *Saulat Pervez, International Institute of Islamic Thought*

Discussant: *Saulat Pervez, International Institute of Islamic Thought*

40.064. Identity, Liberation and Counternarrativity Across Educative Spaces. SIG-Research Focus on Black Education; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304C;
4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

The Future of a Black University, Or Black Education Today. *Zachary R. Brown, SUNY New Paltz*

An Autoethnographic Study: Perspectives on HBCU Graduate Student Advising. *Tryan L. McMickens, North Carolina*

Central University; Regina Gavin Williams, North Carolina Central University

Black First-Generation College Students Visualizing Thriving at Historically White Institutions. *Quaylan Allen, Chapman University*

Joy as Data, Resistance as Assessment: Black Student Photovoice at a Hispanic-Serving Institution. *Lissa Ramirez-Stapleton, California State University - Fullerton*

40.065. Reimagining Community-Based Education Spaces: Interdisciplinary Perspectives on Black Youth and Youth Workers Disrupting the Youthwork Paradox. SIG-

Research Focus on Black Education; Working Group Roundtable

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 501A; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Considerations for Everyday Youth Workers: Broadening the Community-Based Education Landscape through Black Community Member Engagement. *Virginia Downing, University of Kentucky*

Milwaukee's Speaking: Youth Voices Shaping the Past, Present, and Future. *Carl Greer, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Currents of the Wake: A Critical Interpretive Synthesis of the Youth Work Paradox. *Ishmael Miller, Arizona State University*

Worthy by Design: Black Girls Cultivating Love and Civic Memory through Literacy. *Barrett Rosser, Morgan State University*

Chair: *Kaleb Germinaro, University of Illinois at Chicago*

40.066. Research on Higher Education PETE Faculty. SIG- Research on Learning and Instruction in Physical Education; Paper Session

Westin Bonaventure, Level 2, Echo Park; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Thick Skin: The Narratives of Spiritual Black Women in Kinesiology Doctoral Programs. *Leslie Dillon, The Ohio State University; Samuel R. Hodge, The Ohio State University*

Design Thinking: A Catalyst for Technology Integration in Physical Education Teacher Education. *Hung-Ying LEE, National Dong Hwa University; Risto Marttinen, George Mason University; Ching-Wei Chang, National Taiwan Normal University*

Incorporating a Peer Mentoring Model into Physical Education Teacher Education Doctoral Training. *Victoria Shiver, University of New Mexico; Martin Eliseo Cordova Vasquez, University of New Mexico; Sean Fullerton, Towson University; Luis Sanchez Martinez, University of New Mexico; Alexander Eugene Kurtzman, California State University - Northridge; McMarshal Hartzenberg, University of New Mexico; Omphile Hubona, University of*

New Mexico; Karen Lux Gaudreault, University of New Mexico

Socializing the Professoriate: A Scoping Review into and Through Faculty Roles in PETE. *Nicolette Suchon, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Christopher J. Kinder, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Eric Slyvester, University of New Mexico; Kevin Andrew Richards, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Understanding PETE Faculty Members' Perceptions of K-12 Teaching Experience in Higher Education. *Alexander Eugene Kurtzman, California State University - Northridge; Karen Lux Gaudreault, University of New Mexico; Victoria Shiver, University of New Mexico; Kevin Andrew Richards, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Jaimie McMullen, University of Northern Colorado*

Chair: *Emily Jones, Illinois State University*

Discussant: *Erin Elizabeth Centeio, University of Hawai'i at Manoa*

40.067. Understanding and Sustaining Rural Educators: Motivation, Professional Learning, and Workforce Development. SIG-Rural Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum A; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

An Investigation of Rural Communities of Practice through Critical Elementary Social Studies Literature. *Erin McHenry-Sorber, West Virginia University; Sara Lohrman Hartman, Ohio University*

From Isolation to Connection: Strengthening Rural Teacher Collaboration Through Large-scale Virtual Professional Learning. *Martha Inouye, University of Wyoming; Lauren Cabrera, University of Michigan - Dearborn; Min Jung Lee, University of North Dakota; Jenna Gist, Purdue University; Maria Zaman, University of North Dakota; Ryan G. Summers, University of North Dakota*

Have Rural Teachers Surpassed Urban Teachers in Retention Intentions?—A National Empirical Study Based on 16,752 Teachers across 21 Provinces in China. *Tingzhou Li, East China Normal University; Li Xin, East China Normal University*

More than a Calling: Factors that Draw Beginning Teachers in Rural Settings to the Profession. *Christopher J. Rivera, East Carolina University; Travis Lewis, East Carolina University; Crisiane Berry, East Carolina University; Mary Huffman, East Carolina University; Lawrence Hodgkins, East Carolina University*

Supporting Rural Teachers through Place-Based Disease Ecology Curriculum and Professional Development. *Tugba Boz, University of North Dakota; Hilarie B. Davis, Technology for Learning Consortium; Rebekah Hammack, Purdue University; Jamie Cornish, Montana State University; Nora C. Smith, Montana State University*

Chair: *Charles L. Lowery, Virginia Tech*

Discussant: *Jamon H. Flowers, University of Georgia*

40.068. School Climate Considerations Related to Bullying, School-level, and Racial Differences. SIG-School Community, Climate, and Culture; Paper Session Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, La Cienega; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

- Troubling Care: A BlackCrit Analysis of Culturally Relevant Care. *Travis E. Dumas, Rutgers University*
- Developmental Considerations for School Climate Research: Comparing Middle and High School Students' School Perceptions. *Jennifer R. Renick, Michigan State University; Chloe Fann, University of Memphis; Asya Tiani Miles, University of Memphis; Emily Srisarajivakul, University of Memphis*
- Bullying by school staff: Associations with student adjustment and school climate. *Jordan LeAnn Kerere, UVA; Francis H. Lim Huang, University of Missouri; Dewey G. Cornell, University of Virginia; Timothy R. Konold, University of Virginia; Jennifer L. Maeng, University of Virginia*
- Examining Racial Disparities in Elementary School Climate Across Georgia. *Jerome Graham, Michigan State University; Aanchal Gidra, Michigan State University*

40.069. Envisioning Futures in Times of Crisis: Lessons from School-University-Community Partnership Research & Practice. SIG-School, University, Community Collaborative Research; Symposium Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Palos Verdes; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

- Community Mapping at the Turn of the Tide: System-Research that Builds Collaborative Culture and Resiliency. *Leslie A. Lopez, University of California - Santa Cruz*
- Youth Participatory Action Research: Transforming Systems to Address Student Homelessness. *Deborah McKoy, University of California - Berkeley; Ruby Kosewicz-Strickland, University of California - Berkeley*
- Design Tensions in Developing Partnerships in Challenging Circumstances. *Lee Michael Martin, University of California - Davis; J.C. Leapman, University of California - Davis*
- Listening and Co-Creating Knowledge: A Qualitative Analysis of University Student Experiences of YPAR. *Erin Rose Ellison, California State University - Sacramento; Julia Early, California State University - Sacramento; Juan Antonio Juarez, California State University - Sacramento; Vanesa Reyes, California State University - Sacramento; Javier Vega, California State University - Sacramento; Jasleen Ralh, California State University - Sacramento; Paige Richards, Fresno Pacific University*
- Chair: *Travis J. Bristol, University of California - Berkeley*
Discussant: *Angela N. Booker, University of California - San Diego*

40.070. Achieving Culturally Sustaining Science Education: Looking Back and Moving Forward. SIG-Science Teaching and Learning; Symposium Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, San Bernardino; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

- Reconciling Differences: Historical Considerations to Ongoing Tensions between Science Education and Culturally Sustaining Pedagogy. *Lindsay Wells, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Curtis O'Dwyer, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Leema G. Berland, University of Wisconsin - Madison*
- Addressing the Limitations of the Nature of Science Construct to Achieve Culturally Sustaining Pedagogy. *Diane H. Silva Pimentel, Brown University*
- Teaching Nature of Science (NOS) through Cultural Windows: A Framework for Latinx Preservice Science Teachers. *Noushin Nouri, University of Texas - Rio Grande Valley; Maryam Saberi, University of Shiraz*
- Equity-Centered Curricular Customization Model: Supporting teachers in professional learning for expansive science teaching. *Katherine L. McNeill, Boston College; Samuel Lee, California State University - Long Beach; Yang Zhang, Northwestern University; Austin Moore, Boston College; Jason Buell, Northwestern University; Maria A. Moreno Vera, Boston College; Brian J. Reiser, Northwestern University; Brianna Balke, Boston College*
- Chair: *Karen L. Terrell, Loyola University Maryland*
Discussant: *Leema G. Berland, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

40.071. Racial Integration, Belonging and Gaps Across States, Districts and Schools. SIG-Sociology of Education; Paper Session Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 501C; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

- "A Mirror of the School": Representation, Interracial Interaction, and Stereotyping in High School Yearbooks. *Emma Britton Miller, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Thurston Domina, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Deven E. Carlson, University of Oklahoma*
- "I Belong as Much as I Want": Changing Perceptions of Belonging in a Racialized Organization. *Ingrid A. Nelson, Bowdoin College; Fiona Bor, Bowdoin College*
- "I didn't want to tell anybody, no adult": Analyzing School and Social Belonging Among Minoritized Middle and High School Youth. *Sophia Rodriguez, New York University; Dulce Lopez Alvarez, New York University; Melissa Ortiz, New York University*
- Sectoral Convergence or Differentiation? Racial Enrollment Gaps in Charter and District Schools under a Maturing Choice System. *Maggie Wood, Washington University in St. Louis*

Toward a New Environmental (De)Segregation? Student Mobility Following Hurricane Flooding in North Carolina, 2014-2022. *Tyler McDaniel, Stanford University*
Chair: *Linn E. Posey-Maddox, Temple University*

40.072. Parents, Equity, and Implementation of Special Education. SIG-Special and Inclusive Education Research; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum C; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

- Darker Skin, Harsher Discipline: Parental Perspectives on Colorism and ADHD Management in Education. *Ashley B Borjon, University of California - Merced*
Culturally Responsive Parent-Mediated Interventions for Children with ASD in Asia: A Meta-Analysis. *SITI MUSAYAROH, Indiana University Bloomington*
Parent Advocacy Training Program Development for Chinese Immigrant Parents of Young Children with Disabilities. *Eleanor Xiaoxiao Mehta, St. John's University; Lei Huang, University of Georgia*
Cobbling Together Services: Parental Resources Shape Parental Actions within Special Education. *Jennifer R. Cowhy, University of Arkansas*
Implementing SEL with Fidelity: Insights from Rural Special Educators. *Brittany L. Hott, University of Oklahoma; Courtney Beers Dewhirst, University of Oklahoma; Sarah Heiniger, University of Oklahoma*

Chair: *Katrina Arndt, St. John Fisher College*

40.073. Seed and soil: New insights into current individual and school-based approaches to promote teachers' well-being. SIG-Stress, Coping, and Resilience; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304A; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

- Preliminary Results from a Randomized Control Trial of the Healthy Minds Program During Pre-Service Training. *Summer Braun, University of Alabama; Alison Hooper, University of Alabama; Matthew Hirshberg, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Mark T. Greenberg, Pennsylvania State University*
Impact of Mindfulness Practice on Teacher Trainee Stress and Behavior Management in a Simulated Classroom. *Tara Lynn Hofkens, University of Virginia; Summer Braun, University of Alabama; Karime Cameron, University of Virginia; Patricia A. Jennings, University of Virginia*
Together, We SOAR: A Systems-Level Approach to Teacher Well-Being Through Compassion and Human Development Education. *Blake A. Colaianne, Pennsylvania State University; Sebrina L. Doyle Fosco, Pennsylvania State University*
School-based intervention approaches to promote teachers' occupation well-being: A research synthesis. *Gyde*

Wartenberg, Humboldt University - Berlin; Josina Schriek, Humboldt University - Berlin; Justine Stang-Rabrig, TU Dortmund University

Chairs: *Gyde Wartenberg, Humboldt University - Berlin; Justine Stang-Rabrig, TU Dortmund University*

Discussant: *Catherine P. Bradshaw, University of Virginia*

40.074. Modeling and Supporting Self-Regulated and Metacognitive Learning. SIG-Studying and Self-Regulated Learning; Paper Session

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Santa Barbara B; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

- Integrating Latent Profile and Network Analysis to Examine Learning Strategies Among First-Year Middle School Students. *Yewon Kim, Ewha Womans University; Junseo Kim, Korea University; John Jongho Park, Pennsylvania State University; Mihee Park, Auburn University*
Learners' Perceptions of a Technology-Enhanced Personalized Intervention to Support Self-Regulated Learning in Continuing Education. *Yvonne M. Fromm, University of Mannheim; Dirk Ifenthaler, University of Mannheim*
Promoting Metacognitive Problem-Solving Among Non-Calculus-Ready First-Year Engineering Students. *D. Jake Follmer, West Virginia University; Megan Hut, West Virginia University; Lizzie Y. Santiago, West Virginia University*
Temporal Trajectories of Self-Regulation Learning: A Markov-Chain Approach to Modeling and Grouping Student Behaviors. *Shasha Li, McGill University; Tingting Wang, Renmin University of China; Jie Gao, McGill University; Nikki G. Lobczowski, McGill University; Krista R. Muis, McGill University; Adam Kenneth Dubé, McGill University; Susanne P. Lajoie, McGill University*
The Different Metacognitive Effects of Peer-Generated Visual Feedback in Learning by Drawing. *Xiyu Chen, East China Normal University; Zhe Wang, East China Normal University*

Chair: *Elise C. Allen, University of Northern Colorado*

Discussant: *Shaf Ahmed, Utah State University*

40.075. Challenges & Possibilities of Union Organizing in Higher Education. SIG-Teachers Work/Teacher Unions; Workshop

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 504; 4:15-5:45pm

Chair: *Denisha Jones, Defending the Early Years*

Participants: *Brianna Kramer, Southern Utah University; Erin Lee Dyke, Oklahoma State University; Dana Morrison, West Chester University of Pennsylvania*

Discussant: *Denisha Jones, Defending the Early Years*

40.076. Adoption and Resistance: Understanding the Human Factors of AI Integration. SIG-Technology as an Agent of

Change in Teaching and Learning; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum
B; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Barriers to Generative AI Adoption Among Community
College Students: Understanding Hesitancy and Resistance.
Jie Lin, Shanghai Jiao Tong University

Tensions and Possibilities of Generative AI in Higher
Education: Unforgetting History, Imagining Multimodal
Futures. *Anqi He, University College London - IOE*

Social Influence and Disciplinary Variation in Graduate
Students' Acceptance of Generative Artificial Intelligence.
Jie Lin, Shanghai Jiao Tong University

Chair: *Anderson Neal de Andrade, Rutgers University*

Discussant: *Marie K. Heath, Loyola University Maryland*

**40.077. From Single-Item Indicators to Complex Constructs:
Insights into Scale Development and Validation.** SIG-Test
Validity Research and Evaluation; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, San Gabriel A; 4:15-
5:45pm

Participants:

Developing and Investigation the Use of Single-Item Measures
in Integrated STEM Education. *Carina Spreitzer, University
of Klagenfurt; Florian H. Mueller, University of Klagenfurt*

Psychometric Analysis of the ACES-2 Reading Scale - Student
Edition. *Jie Ni, The Pennsylvania State University; Pui-Wa
Lei, Pennsylvania State University; James Clyde Diperna,
Pennsylvania State University*

Measurement Invariance of an Academic Self-Concept Scale.
*Nilay Gunel, Baylor University; Todd Kettler, Baylor
University; Tara Toft, Regional Center for Arts and
Academic Studies; cole sussman, Baylor University*

Chair: *Yuxi Qiu, Florida International University*

Discussant: *Youn Seon Lim, University of Cincinnati*

**40.078. Bridging Worlds of Words: Insights from Bilingual,
Multimedia, and Meta-Analytic Research.** SIG-
Vocabulary; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Beaudry A; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Multimedia Digital Stories and Science Vocabulary Learning in
Preschoolers: The Role of Attention-Guiding Features.
*Claire Seung-Hee Son, University of Utah; Kirsten Butcher,
University of Utah; Ashley Silcox, University of Utah;
Justine Hampton, University of Utah; Gwendolyn Marie
Douglas, University of Georgia*

Profiles of Dual-Language Skills in Spanish-English Emergent
Bilinguals in Dual Language Programs. *Ye Shen, Johns
Hopkins University; Becky H. Huang, The Ohio State
University*

Quality of Shared Book Reading and Home Language
Vocabulary Among Low-Income Preschool-Age Dual
Language Learners. *Emily Mak, Texas A&M University;*

*Qing Zhou, University of California - Berkeley; Yuuko
Uchikoshi, University of California - Davis*

Vocabulary matters beyond reading comprehension: Evidence
from a meta-analysis. *Julian Levine, University of California
- Irvine; Alissa Patricia Wolters, University of California -
Irvine; Young-Suk Grace Kim, University of California -
Irvine*

Chair: *Lori Bruner, University at Albany - SUNY*

Discussant: *Yuuko Uchikoshi, University of California - Davis*

Division and SIG Roundtables

40.079. AERA Roundtable Session Thursday 4:15 pm;
Roundtable Session

**40.079-1. Leadership Without Walls: Virtual, Vocational, and
Cross-Cultural Contexts (Table 1).** Division A -
Administration; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 4:15-
5:45pm

Participants:

A Research Synthesis Examining P-12 Virtual School Leaders.
*Natalie B. Milman, The George Washington University;
Jessa Henderson, University of Bergen*

Leveraging Complex Systems for Flourishing Lives:
Leadership in a Faith-based Singapore School. *Kar-men
Cheng, National Institute of Education - Nanyang
Technological University; Yancy Toh, National Institute of
Education - Nanyang Technological University; Siao-see
Teng, Nanyang Technological University - National Institute
of Education; Uma Natarajan, National Institute of
Education - Nanyang Technological University; Peter Seow,
National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological
University*

Data-Driven Decision Making in Schools: A Comparative Case
Study of Practices and Barriers in Azerbaijan, Estonia, and
Finland. *Sabina Aghayeva, University of Missouri; Ayaz
Karimov, University of Jyväskylä; Se Woong Lee, University
of Missouri*

Chair: *Jeff Walls, University of Iowa*

**40.079-2. Leading the Littlest Learners: Working Toward a
Pre-K Inclusive Research Agenda in Educational
Administration (Table 2).** Division A - Administration;
Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 4:15-
5:45pm

Participants:

The Road Less Traveled: Early Childhood Teachers' Rare
Ascent to the Superintendency and Its Impact on Leadership.
*Rachel Sue White, University of Texas at Austin; Lauren C.
McKenzie, University of Texas at Austin; Christopher P.
Brown, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Jinseok Shin,*

University of Texas at Austin; David E. DeMatthews, University of Texas at Austin

Making a Case for Closing the Superintendent Gap: Strong Early Childhood Education Leadership. *Rachel Sue White, University of Texas at Austin; Lauren C. McKenzie, University of Texas at Austin; Michael H. Little, North Carolina State University; Rachel Rowan, North Carolina State University; Timothy Drake, North Carolina State University*

How Superintendents Make Sense of Leading Public Pre-K Programs. *Rachel Rowan, North Carolina State University; Lora Cohen-Vogel, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Lauren C. McKenzie, University of Texas at Austin*

Chair: *Timothy Drake, North Carolina State University*

Discussant: *Stacey A. Rutledge, Florida State University*

40.079-3. Intersectional Identity Narration, Negotiation, and Masking in School and Community-Based Organizations (Table 3). Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Black LGBT STEM Majors' (In)Visible Identities and Identity Disclosure. *Chandel Burgess, University of Texas at Austin; Nkasano R. Fullerton, University of Texas at Austin*

How Intersectional Identity and Organizational Culture Shape Staff Experiences in a Community-Based Organization. *Kristen Rebecca Cruz, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Lan Quach Kolano, University of North Carolina - Charlotte*

Masking Identity Markers: Ethiopian immigrant youth and white schooling norms. *Eskender A Yousuf, Carnegie Mellon University - Qatar; Awad Ibrahim, University of Ottawa*

Narrating Palestinian Identity, Belonging, and Resistance in U.S. Education. *Orwa Sedawi, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev*

Steering Trajectories of Engagement: Teachers of Color's Identity Negotiation in the First Year of Teaching. *Nathanie A. Lee, University of Washington - Bothell*

Chair: *Orwa Sedawi, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev*

40.079-4. Intersectional Racializations, Gendering, and Caste Across Schooling Contexts (Table 4). Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Intersectional Inequalities and Educational Barriers for Young Syrian Refugee Women Preparing for Higher Education. *Emre Arslan, Ankara University*

Not Just Black, Not Just Immigrant: Intersectional Racialization and African Immigrant Students Experiences. *Mercy Agyepong, New York University*

Reimagining Math Readiness: Equity, Identity, and Belonging Among Black Students in STEM. *Elise A. Simmons, Albany State University*

Social Construction of Caste: Nepali Dalits' Higher Education Experiences from Nepal to the U.S. *Khem Sedhai, University at Albany - SUNY*

Teachers' Perceptions on The Saudi Arabia Co-Education School System And its Impacts. *Reham Alghamdi, Claremont Graduate University*

Chair: *Mercy Agyepong, New York University*

40.079-5. Language, Pláticas, and Testimonios In School and Community (Table 5). Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Duoethnographic Pláticas: Examining Indigeneity and Mestizaje Realities Through an Entre Mundos Praxis. *Erika D. Garcia, University of San Diego; Ymasumac Marañón Davis, University of San Diego*

Haciendo camino al andar: Pláticas with ESOL Community Educators and Organizers. *Dahlia Fabregat, University of Florida*

Turning Fear into Curiosity: A Novice Spanish Teacher's Efforts Toward Enacting Critical Language Pedagogy. *Liv H. Detwiler, East Tennessee State University; James Coda, University of Tennessee*

"We're all collectively fearless": Resisting restrictive language policies to imagine new futures. *Neida Basheer Ahmad, Loyola Marymount University*

Chair: *Neida Basheer Ahmad, Loyola Marymount University*

40.079-6. Critical Educational Research in the Asian Context (Table 6). Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Indischool and Teacher Resistance After the Seoi incident in South Korea. *Gayoung Choi, University of Nebraska - Lincoln; SungEun Min, Kutztown University of Pennsylvania*

South Korea's Village Curriculum: Challenges and Promise for Community-Based Democratic Education. *Shuning Liu, Ball State University; Jaewon Jang, Ball State University*

Transformative Sustainability Learning through a Life History: A Korean Climate Activist's Journey. *HyeJung Shin, Seoul National University*

The Acquisition of Symbolic Capital at Tibetan Supplemental Education Programs in China. *Andrew David Frankel, Denison University*

The Sankofa of Sustaining Agency: Race, Gender & Systemic Tensions in Black Family Early Literacy Codesign. *Ann M. Ishimaru, University of Washington; Sefanit Habtom,*

University of Washington; Dana Gabrielle Nickson, University of Washington; Dawit Endale Alemayehu, University of Washington; Mia Williams, Seattle Public Schools

Chair: *Sohyun An, Kennesaw State University*

40.079-7. Critical Theory in Educational Research and Praxis (Table 7). Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

A Collective Embrace for an Educational Future Worthy of Us All: A Womanist Caring for Thriving. *Sierra Stern, University of Pittsburgh; Keanna Cash, University of Pittsburgh; Michael G. Gunzenhauser, University of Pittsburgh*

Towards a Feminist Carceral Literacies Approach:

Considerations Informed by the Ways of Knowing of Incarcerated Women. *Reka C. Barton, University of Maryland; Naomi Ramirez, San Diego State University; Melissa E. Abeyta, University of Texas - Rio Grande Valley*

A Critical Literature Review: Counternarratives of Queer Youth. *Arisandy Johnson, Arizona State University*

Safe in College, Uncertain in Classrooms: An LGBTQIA+ Community Participatory Action Research Study. *Heather Macias, California State University - Long Beach; Julia Lathin, California State University - Long Beach*

Messy, but Serious : Reimagining the Student Council as Public Space for Student Voice. *Jeongmin Lee, Ewha Womans University, (Republic of Korea)*

Chair: *Alycia M. Elfreich, Montana State University*

40.079-8. Racializing Social Contexts (Table 8). Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

“Double Dutch”: Operationalizing Double Consciousness Among Teachers in the Deep South. *Derric Ivan Heck, Stanford University*

“We’re Ready to Level Up”: Exploring a Cross-Racial Participatory Critical Ethnography. *Abbie Cohen, Colby College*

Where Black Students Thrive—and Where They Don’t: A Dual-Axis Analysis of Achievement and Growth. *Darnell Leatherwood, University of Michigan; Faeze Safari, University of Connecticut; Jennifer Aracely Rodriguez, University of Michigan Ann Arbor*

Who’s Writing About Black Girls? Analyzing Author Positionality in Studies of Black Girls in STEM. *Olayinka Mohorn, University of Memphis; Monica L. Miles, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Demetrice Smith-Mutegi, Old Dominion University; Alexis Riley, New York University;*

Catherine Quinlan, North Carolina Central University; Joi DeShawn Merritt, James Madison University; Crystal Morton, Indiana University - Indianapolis

Chair: *Zachary A. Casey, Rhodes College*

40.079-9. Leadership for Resilience and Equity in Rural and International Contexts (Table 9). SIG-Leadership for School Improvement; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Building Resilient Leadership Networks: Collaborative Approaches to Educational Opportunity in High-Needs Elementary Schools. *Umar Qureshi, University of Toronto; Sofia Malik, University of Texas at Austin; Joseph J. Flessa, University of Toronto - OISE*

Facilitating Critical Conversations to Advance Equity:

R.A.I.S.E. as a K-12 Leadership Tool in Polarizing Times. *Paul Nalli, Arizona State University*

‘If You Want to be a Khan, be With Your People’: Educational Leadership in Rural Schools in Kazakhstan. *Bauyrzhan Kazyiev, Nottingham University*

Leading With a Community Schools Mindset: Competencies and Conditions for Transformative Leadership in Community Schools. *Peter N. Knox, University of Vermont*

Chair: *Samantha L. Viano, George Mason University*

40.079-10. Socially-Just Leadership for Marginalized Identities (Table 10). SIG-Leadership for Social Justice; Roundtable Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Leading with Equity: Supporting School Leaders in Navigating Special Education Practices and Unpacking Implicit Bias. *Kristin Vogel-Campbell, North Point Educational Service Center*

A Review of K-12 Leadership Resistance to Exclusionary LGBTQ+ Policies: A Tempered Radicalism Perspective.

Kody M. Colvin, University of Utah; irene h. yoon, University of Utah; Raven Rylander, University of Utah

From Punitive to Restorative: The Impact of Discipline Policy Reform in Two Central California High Schools. *William Yovanni Marroquin, California State University - Stanislaus;*

Anysia P. Mayer, California State University, Stanislaus; Kim Wood, Ceres Unified School District; Shadi Safi,

Roseville City School District

Leadership Practices in Schools that go Above and Beyond in Support of Black Students. *Decoteau J. Irby, University of Illinois at Chicago; Devin Swartley, Chicago Public Schools; Jason Salisbury, University of Illinois at Chicago;*

David Mayrowetz, University of Illinois at Chicago

Leadership for Liberation Under Repression: Historical Lessons for Navigating Education Attacks and Shaping

Transformative Change. *Cami Touloukian, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Chair: *La Quirshia Fennell, Claremont Graduate University*

40.080. AERA Roundtable Session Thursday 4:15 pm;
Roundtable Session

40.080-1. Reimagining What Works: Critical Perspectives on School Effectiveness and Improvement Research (Table 1). SIG-School Effectiveness and School Improvement; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

A Discriminant Function Analysis of DASS High Schools And Traditional Public High Schools in California. *Anthony Peña, California State Polytechnic University - Pomona*

Effects of Digital Learning Factors on Students' Literacy: Patterns by School Level in South Korea. *Seoyoung Lim, Arizona State University*

Social Work in Schools: Moving Beyond Zero-Tolerance Through Reflective Practice and Policy Reimagination. *Jasmine Scotton, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Kendra Alexander, North Carolina A&T State University*

Early Implementation Outcomes of a Whole-Child School Reform. *Yurou Wang, University of Alabama; Greg Benner, University of Alabama; Sijia Zhang, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Zhehan Jiang, Peking University*

Where are the Gaps? A Systematic Literature Review on Strategies to Address Chronic Absenteeism. *Margaret K. Powers, Washington University in St. Louis; Pallavi Chhabra, Washington University in St. Louis; Melissa C. Molloy, Loyola University Chicago; Abigail C. Medler, Saint Louis University*

Chair: *Robert White, ECSU*

Discussant: *Adejah Taylor, University of California - Los Angeles*

40.080-2. Bilingual Teacher Identity, Agency, and Professional Development (Table 2). SIG-Bilingual Education Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

"Es Lo Que Somos": Overlapping Identities and Resistance in Dual Language Mathematics Professional Development. *Mariana Alvidrez, New Mexico State University; Lidia Herrera-Rocha, EDVantage Analytics LLC; Jennifer Osuna, Stanford University*

"Haciendo La Lucha" Analysis on Texas Elementary Bilingual Spanish Teachers' Language Self-Efficacy: Educator's Own Evaluations and Perceptions of Their Own Spanish. *Citlaly Rivas, Irving Independent School District*

A Phenomenological Exploration of Paradoxical Positioning of a Monolingual Teacher in a Bilingual School. *Zeynep*

Arslan, The Ohio State University; Jae Sonalkar, The Ohio State University

Advancing Critical Consciousness in DLBE: Factors Shaping Collective Teacher Agency in Classroom-Level Curriculum Reform. *Dolores D. Lopez, University of California - San Diego*

40.080-3. Language Ideologies and Policy in Practice (Table 3).

SIG-Bilingual Education Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

New Bilingual Teachers Developing Ideological Clarity to Teach Science and Engineering in K-6. *Alberto Esquinca, San Diego State University; Melissa Arabel Navarro, San Diego State University; Katya Hernandez, San Diego State University; Maraliz Fischler-Barraza, San Diego State University*

Preparing Dual Language Teacher Leaders: Evidence from a Quasi-Experimental Study in Illinois. *Elizabeth L. Adams, American Institutes for Research; Katie Dahlke, American Institute for Research; Erin Mackinney, Roosevelt University; Brenda D. Arellano, American Institutes for Research; Max Pardo, American Institutes for Research*

Reconstructing Perspectives through Bilingual Education History: Pre-Service Teachers in an ESL Endorsement Course. *Hee Young Choi, Millikin University*

Rightful Presence Framing of Translanguaging: Preservice Teachers' Literacy Decisions in a Mixed-Methods Inquiry. *Sumin Lim, Hunter College; Hari Jang, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University; Gregory Cheatham, University of Kansas*

Revoicing and Reclaiming Bilingualism/Multilingualism: Unforgetting the Voices of Bilingual Teachers to Reimagine Teaching and Research Practices in Bilingual Education. *Jorge L. Solis, University of Texas - San Antonio; Brenda Sarmiento-Quezada, Purdue University*

40.080-4. The Impact of Social Context and Language Learning (Table 4). SIG-Bilingual Education Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Understanding Early Care and Education Access for Multilingual Families: A Mixed Methods Study of Program Practices and Provider Decision-Making. *Alain Bengochea, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Gerilyn Slicker, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Melissa Stoffers, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Priscila Hernandez-Anaya, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Leticia Delgado, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Emmanuel Ayitah, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Amanda Zapata, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*

The Impact of School Type and Region on English Language Outcomes in Costa Rica. *Jose Fabian Elizondo-Gonzalez, University of Kansas; Walter Araya Garita, Universidad de Costa Rica*

From Contested Lands to Reclaiming our Land Midwestern Teachers (Re)Storying Dual Language Programs for Latine/x Bilingual Communities. *Enrique David Degollado, Loyola University Chicago; Idalia Nunez, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Blanca Gabriela Caldas Chumbes, University of Minnesota; Andrew Hilton Hurie, University of Wisconsin - Whitewater*

40.080-5. Imagining Histories and Futures of Children and Families (Table 5). SIG-Critical Perspectives on Early Childhood Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Beyond Navigation: Korean Immigrant Mothers as Cultural Advocates in Predominantly White Early Childhood Settings. *Pyeongeeun Kim, Michigan State University*

Construction and Counter-construction of Childhood in Colonial Bengal and Post-colonial Bangladesh. *Md Rifat Hassan Liju, Pennsylvania State University*

Freedom to Control: Parents' Rights in Early Childhood Policy and Ideological Compliance. *Sara Michael-Luna, University of Central Florida*

Navigating Indiana's Non-Universal PreK: How Families and Providers Access and Experience PreK Voucher System. *Jiyeon Lee, Ball State University*

40.080-6. Navigating K-12 Leadership (Table 6). SIG-Research on Women and Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Navigating Dual Domains: A Discourse Analysis of Work-Life Barriers Encountered by Women High School Principals. *Anne Allegretti, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Liv T. Davila, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Reimagining Improvement Science Through the Leadership of Black Women in K-12 Education. *Tamra Simpson, San Bernardino County Superintendent of Schools; Valery Dragon, UnboundEd*

Repairing the Leak: Understanding and Addressing the Gendered Broken Pipeline in School Leadership. *LeAnne C. Salazar Montoya, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Tracie Trinidad, Aurora Public Schools; Paulina Lerma, Denver Public Schools; Cynthia Romero, Nevada Prep Charter School; Sharon Ross, East Texas A&M University; Griselda Galindo-Vargas, Texas State University*

Tapped or Trapped? Investigating Mechanisms That Shape Black Female Teachers' Access to School Leadership Roles.

Francesca Henderson, University of Maryland; Andrew M. Brantlinger, University of Maryland

40.080-7. Under-represented Perspectives in Philosophy of Education (Table 7). SIG-Philosophical Studies in Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Beyond Examination Excellence: Singapore's Education System and Authentic Human Goods. *Sean Chen Liu, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University*

Negativity of Historical Knowledge: Whims of Relativeness. *AnNa Choi, Educator*

The Conscience Justice Theory in Chinese Traditional Culture. *WEI GAO, QuFu Normal University*

The Courage to Question: Bridging Philosophy, Psychology, and Pedagogy Through Doubt. *Stacey E. Robbins, Saint Mary's College of California; Saskia Eschenbacher, Akkon University of Applied Sciences*

40.080-8. Unforgetting the Past and Re-Remembering the Future: Colonial, Postcolonial, and Historical Perspectives on Children's Literature (Table 8). SIG-Literature; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Unforgetting Empire: Vampires and the Violence of Colonial Memory in BIPOC Speculative Fiction. *Christina Salazar, Texas Woman's University; Victor Antonio Lozada, University of North Texas - Dallas; Cassandra Schroeder, University of Nebraska*

Unforgetting Colonialism: A Critical Content Analysis of Indian American Immigrants in Middle Grade Novels. *Danielle Sachdeva, University of North Georgia*

Revisiting Histories to Imagine Futures: A Scoping Review on Reading and Teaching Historical Fiction. *Axa Khalid Warraich, The Ohio State University*

Chair: *Scott Storm, University at Albany - SUNY*

40.080-9. Mapping the Field: Trends, Frameworks, and Global Perspectives in Middle Level Research (Table 9). SIG-Middle-Level Education Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Online Pedagogies in the Middle Grades: A Scoping Review. *Bridget K. Coleman, University of South Carolina - Aiken; Brooke Eisenbach, Lesley University*

Research Synthesis on Global Education: Implications for Middle Grades Research and Practice. *Bogum Yoon, Binghamton University - SUNY*

Trends & Gaps in the Middle: A Content Analysis of MLER Research Agenda Literature Reviews. *Kristina N. Falbe, Illinois State University; Kathleen M. Brinegar, University of Vermont; Matthew J. Moulton, Colorado State University; Cheryl R. Ellerbrock, University of South Florida; Margaret Rintamaa, University of Kentucky*

Validating the Successful Middle School Framework: A Structural Equation Modeling Approach. *Sarah E. Pennington, Montana State University; Christina J. Fassbender, Montana State University*

Middle Level Curriculum in United States Public Schools: A Status Report. *Amanda Wall, Georgia Southern University; Steven B. Mertens, Illinois State University; James F. Nagle, Saint Michael's College; Christopher S. Weiler, Kutztown University of Pennsylvania; Stacie Kae Pettit, Georgia College & State University*

40.081. AERA Roundtable Session Thursday 4:15 pm - Gold 1;
Roundtable Session

40.081-1. New Approaches to Facilitating Student Success (Table 1). Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Equity-Minded Institutional Research as a Catalyst for Sensemaking and Organizational Change. *Holli Ann Tonyan, California State University - Northridge*

Exploring the Role of Relational Trust in Transfer Student Success. *Catherine Hartman, North Carolina State University; Hayden Cunningham, Old Dominion University*

Organizational Resilience in Action: How Faculty Navigate S-STEM Program Implementation Through Adaptive Leadership. *Taylor Lightner, QEM Network; Brittany Boyd, American Institutes for Research; Mercy Mugo, Qem Network; Ivory A. Toldson, Howard University*

Staff Reflections on Learning and Development through Coach Training. *Elizabeth A. Rainey, Loyola University New Orleans; Corina Caraccioli, Louisiana State University; Zach Taylor, John Burton Advocates for Youth*

Chair: *Karina Guerrero, Claremont Graduate University*

40.081-2. Constructing Practice, Shaping Identity: Preservice Teacher Learning Across Disciplines and Dialogues (Table 2). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Constructing History's Future: Cognitive Shifts and Principle Formation in Pre-service Teachers' AI Practice. *Juanjuan Li, East China Normal University; Xiangfang Song, East China Normal University; Yuwei Wei, East China Normal*

University; Dan Wang, East China Normal University; Mingzhuo Liu, East China Normal University

Exploring Teacher Educator Discourse Moves in Elementary Mathematics Teacher Preparation: A Case Study. *Hong Zhang, University of Florida; Melissa M. Soto, University of Florida; Zhihui Fang, University of Florida*

Four Profiles of STEM Teacher Leadership: Leadership Identity, Innovative Teaching, and Leadership Role Enactment. *Seoyeon Park, University of Nevada, Las Vegas; Peter Wiens, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*

Persistent Patterns: How Mathematics Pre-Service Teachers Ask Questions During Simulated Rehearsals. *Sarah Lilly Deans, University of Virginia; Jim Bywater, James Madison University; Caitlyn Hewitt, James Madison University; Jennifer L. Chiu, University of Virginia*

Teacher Educators and Preservice Teachers Constructing Knowledge of New Literacies In A Multi-Institutional Longitudinal Examination. *Tala M. Karkar Esperat, Eastern New Mexico University; Brady L. Nash, University of Florida; Lyudmyla Ivanyuk, Trinity Christian College; Courtney Shimek, West Virginia University; Kathryn M. Pierce, Saint Louis University*

40.081-3. Teaching in the Digital Commons: Care, Community, and Resistance (Table 3). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Exploring Roots of Place and Possibility: Rural Teacher Leaders' Journeys in an Online Community of Practice. *Emily Gleason, University of Colorado - Boulder; Paula Battistelli, University of Colorado - Boulder*

Exploring Teacher Activism in the Age of Digital Resistance. *Ogonna Abraham Onuorah, Montclair State University; Noriko Takahashi, Montclair State University*

Understanding the Development of CS Teacher Identity in a Year-Long Education Program. *Meize Guo, University of Florida; Andrew Bennett, University of Florida; Shan Zhang, University of Florida; Maya Israel, University of Florida*

Chair: *Emily Gleason, University of Colorado - Boulder*

40.081-4. Fractured Narratives, Contested Policies: Critical Analyses of Power in Education (Table 4). Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

A Narrative and Critical Policy Analysis of Providence Public Schools During the State Takeover. *Adrienne C. Goss, Clark Atlanta University*

Framing Higher Education as a Public Good: Narratives, Power, and Policy in Trade Journals. *Antonia Bacigalupa*

Albaum, Indiana University

Freedom and Control: A Critical Discourse Analysis of American Public Schools as Ideological Battlegrounds. *Grace Katzmar, Teachers College, Columbia University*

How Is “Serving the Nation” Articulated? — The Construction of Patriotic Discourse and the Gaps in Policy Implementation in China’s Elite Science Talent Programs. *Sun Xiaoxiao, Peking University; Daozheng Li, Xiamen University*

Taking What Is Left: How District Leaders and Community Members Construct School Closures and Communities. *Tia R. Williams, Vanderbilt University; Kathryn James McGraw, Vanderbilt University*

Chair: *Jennifer Ventimiglia, Northeastern Illinois University*
Discussant: *Judith I. Brooks-Buck, J. Brooks-Buck Educational Consulting*

40.081-5. Understanding Civic Agency and Voice of Higher Education Students (Table 5). SIG-Democratic Citizenship in Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Conditions of Belonging: An Exploration of Political Voice, Discipline, and Belonging in Schools. *Sarah Luria, University at Albany; Tamar Malloy, University of Colorado - Boulder; Marayna Martinez, University of Colorado - Boulder*

Reconceptualizing Civic Agency: An Agentic Analysis of Civic Engagement Practices and Concepts in Higher Education. *Jeff Ching-Fan Lai, University of Iowa*

Reimagining Civic Life: Latinx Students’ Civic Identities in California Community Colleges. *Marisol Avalos, Coast Community*

Chair: *Seonmi Jin, Indiana University*

40.081-6. Leading, Belonging, and Bearing the Weight of Teaching (Table 6). SIG-Lives of Teachers; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

A Study on Teacher Leadership of Teachers on YouTube: The Case of Teachers in Korea. *Moonyoung Eom, Seoul National University*

Disrupting Silos: Unpacking Teacher Leadership in an Out-of-District Community of Practice. *Shanna Dawn Anderson, Montclair State University; John O’Meara, Montclair State University; Timothy Aberle, Montclair State University; Monica Taylor, Montclair State University; Mika Munakata, Montclair State University; Emily J. Klein, Montclair State University*

Investigating Transnational Korean Teachers’ Funds of Identity in the Global Migration Contexts. *Sharon Chang, Teachers*

College, Columbia University; Younghan Kim, Myong Ji University

Moral Distress Among Teachers, Counselors, and School Administrators in the Aftermath of Neighborhood Gun Violence. *Nora Gross, Barnard College; Alexander Pereira, Massachusetts Coalition to Prevent Gun Violence; Anika Lanser, Columbia University; Kelly Yoshimura, Columbia University*

Enhancing Optimal Experiences in the Lives of K–12 Music Educators. *Megan Reilly; Drew Xavier Coles, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Chair: *Kristina M. Valtierra, Colorado College*

40.081-7. Equity, Access, and Targeted Funding in Education Policy (Table 7). SIG-Fiscal Issues, Policy and Education Finance; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Examining Pell Grant Influence on College Completion in Alabama Higher Education. *Moses Oladele Ogunniran, University of Alabama; Hee Jung Gong, University of Alabama; Noel E. Keeney, University of Alabama*

Financing Inclusion, Structuring Inequality? Fiscal Policy in Social Mobility for Rural-to-Urban Migrants in China. *Yangguang Hu, Guangzhou University*

Promotion of a Statewide College Savings Program in the K-12 School Setting. *Flora Zemleni, University of California - Los Angeles; Sabella Tran, University of California - Los Angeles; Mark Hansen, University of California - Los Angeles*

The Impact of Special Education Funding Caps on Identification and Equity: A Case Study of Washington State. *Tammy Kolbe, American Institutes for Research; Elizabeth Dhuey, University of Toronto - Scarborough*

Chair: *Mariano Lozano-Soto, San Diego State University*

40.081-8. The role of Policy and Law in Shaping Solutions to Problem of Practice in Schooling (Table 8). SIG-Law and Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Centering Place and Space in Recurrent Citations for Racial Disproportionality in Special Education. *Alexandra Aylward, University of Nevada - Reno; Catherine Kramarczuk Voulgarides, Hunter College - CUNY*

Not Quite Public: Legal Framing and Transparency in School Choice Marketing Across New Jersey. *Steven Michael Carlo, Monmouth University*

How Special Education Litigation Takes Place: An Example from Baltimore, Maryland. *Joel Miller, University of Maryland*

Special Education Due Process in Nevada: Spatial and

Temporal Trends and Implications for Policy. *Alexandra Aylward, University of Nevada - Reno; Ruby Batz, University of Nevada - Reno*

The Dangerous Illusion of School Safety. *Terry Allen, Ph.D., J.D., USC Gould School of Law*

Chair: *Natasha N. Johnson, Augusta University*

40.081-9. Policy Analysis Across Contexts (Table 9). SIG-

Politics of Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

A Cross National Analysis of Public Opinion on the Role of Government in Education. *Hinako Miyazaki, Michigan State University*

Chilling classrooms: How “Don’t Say Gay” laws influence teacher retention and professional identity. *Kathryn Watson, Appalachian State University; Chris Patterson, University of Iowa*

Cultivating Desire and Common Sense: teachers as architects of the self and governmentality. *Zahid Naz, Queen Mary University of London*

School Board Decision Making: The Impact of State Polices. *Meredith L. Mountford, Florida Atlantic University*

40.082. AERA Roundtable Session Thursday 4:15 pm - Gold 2;
Roundtable Session

40.082-1. Study Abroad/International/Global (Table 1).

Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Crossing Borders, Graduating Students: A Transborder Graduation Model in Higher Education at the U.S.-Mexico Borderlands. *Vannessa Falcón Orta, San Diego State University; Gilberto Reyes, San Diego State University; Carlos Fitch, University of California - Santa Barbara; Efren Lopez, San Diego State University*

College Academic Outcomes and Knowledge about Higher Education. The Adverse Effects of High-School Tracking in Chile. *Maria Veronica Santelices, Catholic University of Chile; Ximena Catalan, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile; Juan Acevedo, University of the Andes; Alicia Ibañez, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile; Magdalena Zarhi, Duoc UC*

Reflexive Agency in Chinese International Students’ Transitions from High Schools to Universities in Anglophone settings. *Yu Hao, University of Oxford*

Chair: *Vanessa Hammler Kenon, University of Texas - San Antonio*

40.082-2. Teacher Learning While Leading: Identity,

Belonging, and Storytelling (Table 2). Division K -

Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Elevating Practice from Within: The Impact of Teacher Leaders on Instruction. *Handrea A. Logis, National Institute for Excellence in Teaching; Tanee Hudgens, National Institute for Excellence in Teaching; Rhea Rong Ren, National Institute for Excellence in Teaching; Joshua H. Barnett, National Institute for Excellence in Teaching*

Extending the Short Critical Consciousness Scale: Measuring Critical Action Among K–8 In-Service Teachers. *Shannon O. Sampson, University of Kentucky; Susan Cantrell, University of Kentucky; Olukemi Olubunmi Kolawole, University of Kentucky; Kristen H. Perry, University of Kentucky*

“It’s a Good Struggle”: Supporting Critical Professional Development, Teacher Agency and Activism in Hostile Times. *Alison G. Dover, California State University - Fullerton; Kira LeeKeenan, California State University - Fullerton*

Teacher-led Trauma-informed Professional Learning Communities as Models of Care and Reflective Action. *Carly Berwick, Montclair State University*

Chair: *Sophie Rebecca Korn Gallagher, Los Angeles County Office of Education*

40.082-3. Empowering In-Service Teachers Through

Professional Development (Table 3). Division K -

Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

A Principle-Based Knowledge Building Approach to Teacher Professional Development for Innovative Teaching. *Cing-Sin Lin, National Chengchi University; Guo-Tsai Hung, National Taichung University of Science and Technology; Chih-Hsuan Chang, National Kaohsiung University of Science and Technology; Mei-Ju Chen, National Tsing Hua University; Huang Yao Hong, National Chengchi University*

Collaborative Inquiry Communities: Teachers’ Stories for Professional Development. *Nneka Ebele Nwaokor, University of North Dakota*

Empowering In-Service Teachers: A Career-Stage–Tailored Professional Development Model to Enhance Self-Efficacy in Teaching Multilingual Learners with Disabilities. *Jocelyn Belden, Georgia State University*

Imagining the Future of Teacher Professional Development: Academic Summer Camps as Catalysts for Teacher Growth. *Robert B. Marsteller, Delaware State University; Tina Mitchell, Delaware State University*

Inequitable Access to Professional Development Opportunities for Teachers of Students with Disabilities. *Wynta Korin*

Nivens, Brooklyn College; Fritz Sannon-Brown, Brooklyn College

Chair: *Sheila Stefany Coli, District 428*

40.082-4. Culture Wars, Curriculum Battles, and Public Schools (Table 4). Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Defending Educational Justice Through Critical Research-Practice-Policy Partnerships: Reflections from a Visioning Process. *Danfeng Soto-Vigil Koon, University of San Francisco; Joseph J. Ferrare, University of Washington Bothell; Huriya Jabbar, University of Southern California*

The Networks and Organizing Efforts of Far-Right Movements in California Schools. *Huriya Jabbar, University of Southern California; Danfeng Soto-Vigil Koon, University of San Francisco; Michael Grigsby, University of Southern California; Tara Blagg, University of Southern California; Daniel Espinoza, University of Southern California; Cecelia Jordan, University of Texas at Austin*

White Christian Nationalism: A Framework for Understanding Ideological Resistance. *Katelin G. Trautmann, Pennsylvania State University*

Organizing to Resist the Far Right. *Natosha Folarin Daniels, University of Texas at Austin; Lisa Vahey, Honesty for Ohio Education; Liv Cook, Statewide Organizing for Community Empowerment; sharon Kirsch, Save Our Schools Arizona Network*

Chair: *Huriya Jabbar, University of Southern California*

Discussants: *Gary L. Anderson, New York University; Leah Watson, American Civil Liberties Union*

40.082-5. Becoming Teachers: Identity, Narrative, and Pedagogical Journeys (Table 5). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Becoming-STEMM Educator-With a Haunted Kindergarten Classroom Apparatus. *Katherine Ayers, St. Jude Children's Research Hospital; Robyn Pennella, St. Jude Children's Research Hospital; Hailey Wolfe, St. Jude Children's Research Hospital*

Listening vs. Storytelling: Effects of Narrative Modes on Pre-Service Teacher Identity and Neural Mechanisms. *Lisha Liu, Beijing Normal University; Saidi Yu, Beijing Normal University; Mengyuan Liu, Beijing Normal University*

Navigating Emotion and Agency in Study Abroad: Identity Journey Mapping as a Tool. *Hyesun Cho, University of Kansas; Josh Hayes, University of Kansas*

Reading Between the Lines: LGBTQ+ Secondary Preservice Teachers' Navigations and Apertures of Teacher-Self.

Summer Davis, Western Michigan University; Bradley Reinbolt, University of Cincinnati

Teacher Collaboration, Open and Shut. *Jeremy T. Murphy, College of the Holy Cross*

Chair: *Hyesun Cho, University of Kansas*

40.082-6. Technological Futures of Arts and Learning (Table 6). SIG-Arts and Learning; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

From Canvas to Code: Using AI to Inspire Creativity in the Art Classroom. *Eun-Ok Baek, California State University - San Bernardino; Chang Liu, California State University - San Bernardino*

Technology-Enhanced Arts Pedagogies: Using the Learning Designer Tool in Blended and Online Learning Environments. *Nikleia Eteokleous, Frederick University; Victoria Pavlou, Frederick University*

Three Case Studies of Digital Twin Museums: Investigating Educational Access and Cultural Mediation. *Qianyu Zhou, Teachers College, Columbia University; Yihui Jiao, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Journeys of Drama Activities in STEAM Education. *Giedre Straksiene, Klaipeda University*

STEAM Research and Education in the Field of Art Education. *Alice Lai, Empire State College - SUNY; Yichien Cooper, Washington State University - Tri-Cities*

Chair: *Yichien Cooper, Washington State University - Tri-Cities*

40.082-7. Self-Studies of Critical Transformations in Teacher Education (Table 7). SIG-Self-Study of Teacher Education Practices; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

It Begins With Us: A Self-Study, Critical Friendship Exploration of Racial Literacy in Teacher Education. *Tara Kirton, Hunter College - CUNY; Yvette M. Regalado, University of Texas - San Antonio*

Restorying Ourselves as Transcultural Teacher Educators: Collaborative Autoethnography as a Site of Transformation. *Seunghoon Han, University of Northern Iowa; Chen Su, Penn State University; Yue Qi, Pennsylvania State University*

Theory Making for (Re)Conscientizing Social Justice in Teacher Education Practice. *Joaquin Arguello, University of New Mexico; Mary F. Rice, University of New Mexico*

Transformational Self-Care: A Higher Education in Prisons Initiative Self-Study. *LaChan V Hannon, Rutgers University - Newark; Ashley N. Gwathney, Rutgers University - Newark; Chris Agans, Rutgers University - Newark; Nia Tuckson, Rutgers University - Newark; Christina Walling, Rutgers University - Newark; Latoya Hamlin, Rutgers*

University - Newark

Chair: Gayle A. Curtis, Texas A&M University

40.082-8. Sovereignty, Refusal, and Relational Pedagogies: Indigenous Frameworks of Accountability, Love, and Responsibility in Education (Table 8). SIG-Indigenous Peoples of the Americas; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Woven with Refusal: From Resistance to Sovereignty through Indigenous Presence and Love. *Kelly Leah Stewart, University of California, Los Angeles*

Relational Pedagogies and Living Sovereignty: Reclaiming Indigenous Histories in Education. *Lydia Nganga, University of Wyoming; John Kambutu, University of Wyoming; Sergio Maldonado, University of Wyoming*

Creating a Sense of Belonging utilizing Indigenous theory's four R's: Respect, Responsibility, Relevance and Reciprocity. *Adolfo Velasquez, San Francisco State University*

Native Tuition Waivers: Honoring the Sovereignty of Native Students Rights to Education. *Robin Zape-tah-hol-ah Minthorn, University of Oklahoma; Natalie Rose Youngbull, University of Oklahoma; Patricia McDaniels-Gomez, University of Oklahoma; Noetta Harjo, University of Oklahoma*

Chair: M. Nathan Tanner, University of Nevada - Reno

40.082-9. Systems of Access: Structural Inequities and Opportunity Pathways Across Science, Literacy, and Mathematics (Table 9). SIG-Access, Detracking, and Tracking; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

A Comparative Group Analysis of Rigorous Science and In School Suspension Odds. *Kristian Edosomwan, University of Houston; Syahrul Amin, Texas A&M University; Jarrod G. Collins, Texas A&M University*

Mathematical Pathways and Barriers: How Tracking Systems Affect Multilingual Learners' Access to Advanced Coursework in Utah. *Marieke Timmer, University of Utah*
Policy, Place, and Possibility: Dual Enrollment Access, Growth, and Equity Challenges in California's Central Valley. *Zenaida Aguirre-Munoz, University of California - Merced; Vandeen Campbell, Rutgers University - Newark; Liantao Shan, University of California - Merced*

Unforgetting Educational Debt: Structural Drivers of Literacy Inequities for Multilingual Learners. *Diana L. Mindrila, University of West Georgia; Robert A. Griffin, University of West Georgia*

Discussant: *Kristian Edosomwan, University of Houston*

40.083. AERA Roundtable Session Thursday 4:15 pm - Gold 4;
Roundtable Session

40.083-1. Learning in Practice: Student Voices, Shared Governance, and Organizational Learning in a Multi-College Research Practice Partnership (Table 1). SIG-Research Use; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Investigating Organizational Learning at a California Community College in a Research Practice Partnership with UCLA. *Kristine Oliveira, Antelope Valley College*

Building the Conditions for Equity-Focused Inquiry: Facilitating a Research Practice Partnership at a Community College. *Lynn Kim-John, University of California - Los Angeles; Kristine Oliveira, Antelope Valley College*

When the Numbers Are Not Enough: Qualitative Student Voice, Institutional Data, and the Conditions for Change. *Michael Davis, Glendale Community College; Kristine Oliveira, Antelope Valley College*

Chair: *Kristine Oliveira, Antelope Valley College*

Discussant: *Lynn Kim-John, University of California - Los Angeles*

40.083-2. Teachers and Children Responding to Policy and Political Contexts Through Multiple Literacies (Table 2). SIG-Writing and Literacies; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Form Letters, Canvassing, and TikTok: How Teachers Use Literacy to Respond to Policy. *Katharine Hull, University of South Florida*

"Stop Banning Books": A Multimodal Analysis of Two Fifth-Grade Students' Co-Authored Protest Comic. *Stephanie F. Reid, University of Cincinnati; Mengying Xue, University of Missouri*

Making Space & Mourning Place: Children's Placemaking Literacies During an Elementary School Closure. *Kristin Valle Geren, University of South Florida*

Chair: *Kerry H. Alexander, University of Maryland*

40.083-3. Motivation, Mindsets, and AI: Understanding Learner Attributes in AI-Enhanced Education (Table 3). Division C - Learning and Instruction; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

CTRL + THINK: Changing STEM Students' Attitudes about Using AI in Learning-Centered Ways. *Carlton J. Fong, Texas State University; Pedram Zarei, Texas State University; Zachary Baquet, University of Houston; Stephen Oluwaseyi Maku, Texas State University; IMANEH SOLEIMANI, Texas State University; Zohreh Fathi, Texas*

State University; Pegah Peimani, Texas State University
 From acceptance to achievement: Exploring learners' perceptions of GenAI tools in EFL learning. *Zhenlei Huang, Shanghai International Studies University; Hui Jin, Shanghai International Studies University*
 Investigating the Drivers of Generative AI Help-Seeking: Structural Equation Model of Attitudes, Norms, and Control. *Andrea Macias, University of Southern California; Stephen J. Aguilar, University of Southern California*
 Motivation, Belonging, and Perceptions of School Work Behind High School Students' AI Usage Patterns. *Ruishi Chen, Stanford University; Sarah Miles, Challenge Success; Annie Camey Kuo, Stanford University; Denise C. Pope, Stanford University; Victor R. Lee, Stanford University*
 Pathways to Proficiency: Mapping the Structural Relationships of Personal Attributes in AI-Integrated Self-Directed Language Learning. *Belle Li, Purdue University; Zhuo Zhang, Towson University; Victoria Lynn Lowell, Purdue University*
 Chair: *Qiuying Wang, Oklahoma State University*

40.083-4. RT6: Tutorials, Guides and Workflows in Quantitative Education Research: Putting our Quantitative Advances into Practical Use (Table 4). Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Roundtable Session
 JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:
 A Bayesian Multilevel Modeling Workflow for Robust Quantitative Inference in Education Research. *M. Shane Tutwiler, University of Rhode Island; Qingyu Yang, University of Rhode Island; Yiping Zhang, University of Rhode Island*
 Propensity Score Matching in Multilevel Educational Settings: A Review and Guide for Applied Researchers. *Jordan Rickles, University of California - Los Angeles; Alberto Guzman-Alvarez, American Institutes for Research; Qi Zhang, American Institutes for Research*
 Fine-Tuning Generative Models for Text Summarization with Limited Data - A Practical Guide. *Zhifei Li, University of Iowa; Li Zhu, University of Iowa; Ariel M. Aloe, University of Iowa; Kishlay Jha, University of Iowa*
 Webscraping as Educational Research Methodology: Innovations, Ethics, and Applications. *Luke Parker, Australian Catholic University*
 Integration of Generative AI in Research Methodology: Graduate Students' Perspectives. *Miluska Jackeline Madelaine Pajuelo Abanto, Universidad Nacional de Trujillo; Aurea Elizabeth Rafael Sánchez, National University of Trujillo; José Ismael Castillo Navarro, National University of Trujillo; Cecilia Del Pilar Vasquez Mondragón, National University of Trujillo; ANTHONY Joel GONZALES PACHECO, National University of Trujillo;*

Víctor Yury Bazán Pajuelo, National University of Trujillo

40.083-5. Method in Transition: Ethics, Temporality, and AI in Evolving Qualitative Research Landscapes (Table 5). Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Roundtable Session
 JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:
 Research Methods for Liminal Times: Investigating Education's Past, Present, and Future through Three Qualitative Approaches. *Chi Nguyen, University of Arizona*
 Ethics in the Algorithm: Artificial Intelligence and Qualitative Research. *Lorien S. Jordan, University of South Florida; Jennifer R. Wolgemuth, University of South Florida; Matthew Weirick Johnson, University of South Florida; Camryn; T. Collins, University of South Florida - Tampa*

40.083-6. Innovating Evaluation: Data-Driven Approaches to Understanding Impact (Table 6). Division H - Research, Evaluation and Assessment in Schools; Roundtable Session
 JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:
 Estimating the Treatment Effect Heterogeneity of Providing Performance Information in Education: A Causal Forests Approach. *Xinjie Zhang, Vanderbilt University; Yi Wei, Peking University; Yingquan Song, Peking University*
 Evaluating Arts-based Program Impact Through Teachers' Perceptions: A Latent Profile Analysis. *Xiaobo Wei, University of South Carolina; Ashlee A. Lewis, University of South Carolina; Dalisha Shingler, University of South Carolina*
 How do Pre-K funding trajectories shape later academic outcomes, and for whom? *Yu Bai, Duke University; Kenneth A. Dodge, Duke University; Jade M. Jenkins, University of California - Irvine; Tyler Watts, Teachers College, Columbia University; Siobhan O'Muircheartaigh, Duke University*
 Scaling Digitally-Supported Innovations to Accelerate Learning from Within the Instructional Core: A Mixed-Methods Evaluation. *Beth R. Holland, FullScale; Megan Benay, FullScale; Rae Lymer, FullScale*
 Chair: *Kavya Sree Mariboyina, Little Priest Tribal College*

40.083-7. Language, Equity, and Meaning-Making in Assessment for Multilingual Learners: Global Perspectives (Table 7). Division H - Research, Evaluation and Assessment in Schools; Roundtable Session
 JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:
 Translanguaging Assessment for Equitable Evaluation in K-12 Classrooms: A Global Scoping Review. *Yi Zhang,*

University of Houston; Miao Li, University of Houston; Xincui Zhang, University of Houston; Marie Carmel Balcos, University of Houston

From Confusion to Clarity: Improving a K-12 ELP Assessment Score Report for Parents. *Jason A. Kemp, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Alicia Kim, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Fujiuju Chang, N/A; Fabiana MacMillan, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Revisiting Speaking Assessment Rubric Design: An Ecological Language Competencies (ELC) Perspective. *Peichang He, The Education University of Hong Kong; Paul Thibault; Angel Mei Yi Lin, The Education University of Hong Kong; Yanyan Sheng, University of Chicago; Xiaoyan Ren, Tianshui Normal University; Yiqi Liu, The Education University of Hong Kong*

Language of Assessment Matters: A Study of Ghanaian Primary School Students' Scientific Reasoning Skills. *Augustine Owusu Achiaw, Clemson University; Edwin Nii Bonney, Clemson University; Kafayat Amoke Adesina, Clemson University; Oluwafemi Osho, Clemson University; Gertrude Arthur, University of Missouri; Lauretta Osho, Clemson University*

Chair: *Jason A. Kemp, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

40.083-8. Qualitative Inquiry in the Age of AI: Reflexivity, Collaboration, Cultural Responsiveness, and a Counter Balance (Table 8). SIG-Qualitative Research; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

The Promise of AI-Assisted Qualitative Analysis in Educational Research: An Example of Thematic Analysis. *Thi Phuong Vy Nguyen, National Taiwan Normal University; Ying-Shao Hsu, National Taiwan Normal University; Hsun-Yu Chan, National Taiwan Normal University; Yi-Fang Lee, National Taiwan Normal University; Hoang Bao Ngoc Nguyen, National Taiwan Normal University; Ching Hsu, National Taiwan Normal University; Hsiao-Ping Yu, National Taiwan Normal University; Kai-Lin Yang, National Taiwan Normal University*

Qualitative Research in the Age of AI: Insights on Culturally Responsive, Community-Engaged Inquiry. *Jori N. Hall, University of Illinois at Chicago; Kwame Poku-Acheampong, University of Illinois Chicago*

Slowing Down Qualitative Data Visualization: Exploring Image Data with the Pointillizer. *Deborah Silvis, SUNY - College at Cortland; Ben Rydal Shapiro, Georgia State University*

Chair: *Mahjabin Chowdhury, Texas A&M University*

40.083-9. Equity, Inclusion and Systemic Challenges in Early Childhood Education (Table 9). SIG-Early Education and Child Development; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

From Survival to Thriving: Portrayal of Child Maltreatment in Picturebooks with Non-human Characters. *Su-Jeong Wee, California State University - Los Angeles; Chelsea Camila Leyva, California State University - Los Angeles*

Dynamic Realities of School Readiness: Challenging the Dichotomous Rhetoric before the Transition to Primary Education. *OURANIA ANASTASIOU; Loizos Symeou, European University Cyprus*

Unforgetting Inequities, Imagining Possibilities: Examining Language Modeling in CLASS and Its Impact on Pre-K Teaching. *Joy L Hernandez, Hampton University; Abha Gupta, Old Dominion University*

Rights Delayed, Rights Denied: Tracing and Transforming Special Education Services in Universal Pre-K. *Maria Mavrides Calderon, Hunter College - CUNY; Raquel Stephen, Hunter College; Sara K Edwards, Hunter College*

Chair: *Maria Mavrides Calderon, Hunter College - CUNY*

40.083-10. STEM, Motivation, and Pathways (Table 10).

Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Does Exposure to Science Museums or Planetariums Shape Science Identity and STEM Major Choice? Evidence from HSLS:09. *Shuhan Ai, University of California - Los Angeles*

Tracing Structural Inequalities in STEM: A Longitudinal Survival Analysis of Gendered and Stratified Higher Education Pathways (2008–2024). *Francisca Beroiza-Valenzuela, Universidad de las Américas (UDLA), Chile*

Validating the Latent Variable Structure of College-Going Motivation, Knowledge, and Behaviors. *Tianlan Wei, Mississippi State University; Judith L. Meece, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Carol Cutler White, Mississippi State University*

Revolutionizing Access: The Early College Model as a Lever for Educational Equity. *Yune Kim Tran, Providence College; Jessica Geier, Providence College; Omari Walker, New Heights Charter School Brockton*

Division and SIG Posters

40.084. AERA Poster Session Thursday 4:15pm; Poster Session

40.084-1. Designing for Dialogue in Science Learning. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 4:15-5:45pm

Posters:

1. Characterizing Discourse Quality in Preschool Science

Education: Toward an Observation Framework (Poster 1). *Zhiyi Han, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Oi-Lam Ng, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Yongjia Yu, University of Hong Kong*

2. Designing Effective Prompts for Eliciting Scientific Argumentation: A Systematic Review (Poster 2). *Zhaoji Wang, University of Hong Kong; ZIPEI ZHU, University of Georgia; Yizhu Gao, University of Georgia; Jongchan Park, Arizona State University; Lihua Tan, University of Macau; Field Watts, Educational Testing Service; Lei Liu, Educational Testing Service; Xiaoming Zhai, University of Georgia*
3. Illuminating Spatial Brilliance Through A Culturally and Linguistically Sustaining Approach to Formative Assessment (Poster 3). *Shakhnoza Kayumova, University of Massachusetts - Dartmouth; Akira Harper, University of Massachusetts - Dartmouth; Esma Nur Kahveci, University of Massachusetts - Dartmouth*
4. Integrating Disciplinary Literacy Strategies into Inquiry-based Middle School Science Instruction (Poster 4). *Raju Ahmed, University of Houston; Jie Zhang, University of Houston; Sissy S. Wong, University of Houston; Laveria Hutchison, University of Houston; Samuel Katende, University of Houston*
5. Peer Interaction and Conceptual Development: A Multimodal Interaction Analysis (Poster 5). *John Galisky, University of California - Santa Barbara*
6. Piloting Case-Based Collaborative Learning in Secondary Health Science Classrooms: Insights from Teachers and Students (Poster 6). *Meghan Ecker-Lyster, University of Kansas; Maya Rose Watkins, University of Missouri - Kansas City; Maria Alonso Luaces, University of Kansas Medical Center; Elizabeth Ordonez, University of Kansas Medical Center; Karin Chang, University of Missouri - Kansas City*
7. Visual representations as resources for discussion between peers in middle school science (Poster 7). *Elon Langbeheim, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev; Einat Ben-Eliyahu, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev*

40.084-2. Investigating the Impact of Title IX Sexual Harassment Policies on the K-12 Experience. Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Poster Session Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 4:15-5:45pm

Poster:

8. Investigating the Impact of Title IX Sexual Harassment Policies on the K-12 Experience (Poster 8). *Megan Swajda-Hardy, Texas A&M University; John A. Williams, Texas A&M University; Quinita D. Ogletree, Texas A&M University*

40.084-3. Critical Examination of Race, Ethnicity, Class, and Gender Poster Session. SIG-Critical Examination of Race,

Ethnicity, Class and Gender in Education; Poster Session Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 4:15-5:45pm

Posters:

9. Analysis of women Images in Chinese State-compiled Senior High School History Textbooks (Poster 9). *Yun Zhang, East China Normal University*
10. Black Hair as Battleground: Black women educators, embodied colonization, and disembodied voyeurism (Poster 10). *Eghosa Obaizamomwan-Hamilton, Stanford University*
11. Confronting hoteps: Addressing theoretical misconceptions of Afrocentricity and exploring African-centered school models for Black students and communities (Poster 11). *Marcia J. Watson-Vandiver, Towson University*
12. Gender Representation in Instructional Materials: A Study of Chinese MRL Textbooks and Teachers' Voices (Poster 12). *Jiaxin WANG, The Education University of Hong Kong; Huixuan Xu, The Education University of Hong Kong*
13. "I just get a different feeling in this class": Affective Belonging in Student-Teacher Encounters at a Dutch Urban Secondary School (Poster 13). *Zehra Colak, Utrecht University*
14. Mandarin for Whom? A Critical Review of Representation in Integrated Chinese (Poster 14). *Yuzi Gao, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*
15. Measuring Whiteness-Informed Practices in K-12 Classrooms: Validation of the Classroom Whiteness Scale (ClaWS) Using Rasch Partial Credit Modeling (Poster 15). *Jaylene Patterson, University of Kentucky*
16. Negotiating Class, Mobility, and Social Capital: Transnational Practices of Chinese Master's Students in the UK (Poster 16). *Xiaolin Ma, University of Manchester*
17. "Othermothering in Crisis: Women of Color Leading K-12 Schools with Care in COVID-19" (Poster 17). *Barbara Mensah, University of Alabama; Shena Sanchez, University of Alabama*
18. The Analytic of Oppression (Poster 18). *Dennis Williams, University of Virginia; Kristyn Wilson, University of Virginia*
19. The Nordic Myth in Education: Performing Transnational Whiteness through Other-Making (Poster 19). *Woomok Jeong, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Dugyum Kim, University of Minnesota; Younkyung Hong, Ball State University*
20. "There's Nothing Really There": Meaning-Making Around the Salience of Race and Identity Among White Adolescents (Poster 20). *Tina M. Durand, Boston University; Mitali Temurnikar, Boston University; Pei Wang, Boston University*
21. The Silence of Whiteness in Teacher Education: A Cross-Case Analysis of Five Teacher Educators (Poster 21). *Allison DeVoe Karcher, Siena College*
22. Who's Missing? Equipping Teachers to Rethink Representation in Classroom Books (Poster 22). *Lesley S. Noel, University of Colorado - Colorado Springs; Aimee*

Frier, Florida State University - Panama City

40.084-4. Looking Back: College Students' Recollections of Parental Academic Socialization. SIG-Family, School, Community Partnerships; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 4:15-5:45pm

Poster:

23. Looking Back: College Students' Recollections of Parental Academic Socialization (Poster 23). *Besjane Krasniqi, University of Maryland - Baltimore County; Susan Sonnenschein, University of Maryland - Baltimore County*

40.084-5. Rethinking Graduate Education: Power, Play, and Well-Being. SIG-Graduate and Postdoctoral Education across the Disciplines; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 4:15-5:45pm

Poster:

24. Gamification of graduate mentoring: What the academy can learn from video games (Poster 24). *Carlson Coogler, Baylor University; Stephanie Anne Shelton, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*

40.084-6. The Parent Power and Leadership Project: Transforming Families Through Community Organizing. SIG-Grassroots Community and Youth Organizing for Educational Justice; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 4:15-5:45pm

Posters:

25. Parent Leadership and Organizing for Justice: A National Landscape Analysis (Poster 25). *Joanna D. Geller, New York University*
26. Building Bridges Between Families, Schools, and Systems for Lasting Change in Massachusetts (Poster 26). *Danielle M. Perry, New York University*
27. "If We Come Together Then We Have Power:" Illinois Parents and Families Leading Across Communities (Poster 27). *Jennifer Cossyleon, Community Change*
28. Centering Cultural Knowledge and Identity: Latine Indigenous Families Building Power with MICOP (Poster 28). *Wendy Y. Perez, NYU Metro Center; Liliana Manriquez, Mixteco Indígena Community Organising Project (MICOP)*
29. Building Strong Families and Early Childhood Education Systems with the Washington State Parent Ambassadors (Poster 29). *Sara McAlister, New York University*
30. "I am because you are." Challenging Injustice and Strengthening Community with Families in NOLA (Poster 30). *Danielle M. Perry, New York University*

Chair: *Joanna D. Geller, New York University*

40.084-7. Empowering Communities through Informal

Engineering Education: A Systematic Literature Review. SIG-Informal Learning Environment Research; Poster Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 4:15-5:45pm

Poster:

31. Empowering Communities through Informal Engineering Education: A Systematic Literature Review (Poster 31). *Chih Hsuan Lin, University of Florida; Andrea Ramirez-Salgado, University of Florida; Pasha Antonenko, University of Florida*

40.084-8. Hidden in Plain Sight: Increasing Museum Sustainability Through Reimagining Trails and Landmarks. SIG-Informal Learning Environment Research; Poster Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 4:15-5:45pm

Poster:

32. Hidden in Plain Sight: Increasing Museum Sustainability Through Reimagining Trails and Landmarks (Poster 32). *Julie Henry, Pennsylvania State University; Ty Hollett, Pennsylvania State University*

40.084-9. Immigration as Learning and Becoming: A Critical Review of Existing Literature. SIG-Informal Learning Environment Research; Poster Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 4:15-5:45pm

Poster:

33. Immigration as Learning and Becoming: A Critical Review of Existing Literature (Poster 33). *Seda Musaoglu Aydin, Simon Fraser University; Engida Hailye Gebre, Simon Fraser University*

40.084-10. Research in Research and Literacy (SIG 11) Poster Session II. SIG-Research in Reading and Literacy; Poster Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 4:15-5:45pm

Posters:

34. College Students' Perceptions of Quality, Veracity, and Source in Human-Written and AI-Generated News Articles (Poster 34). *Goeun Na, Hanyang University; Soo-hyun Im, Hanyang University*
35. Does Multilingualism Lift All Boats? Literacy Trajectories in Ontario Schools (Poster 35). *Jeanne Sinclair, Memorial University of Newfoundland; Scott Davies, University of Toronto - OISE; Paul Lefebvre, McMaster University; Hyunah Kim, Education Quality and Accountability Office; Ling Li, University of Prince Edward Island; Magdalena Janus, McMaster University*
36. Expanding the Tools and Scope of Early Literacy Assessments: The Parent-based Assessment of Literate

Identities (Poster 36). *Christopher Wagner, Santa Clara University*

37. Exploring the Roles of Text and Images in Primary Students' Multimodal Reading Comprehension of Informational Materials (Poster 37). *Yaping Liu, The Hong Kong Polytechnic University; Xinhua Zhu, Hong Kong Polytechnic University; Choo Mui Cheong, University of Hong Kong*
38. Linguistic and cognitive predictors of listening comprehension among early elementary students (Poster 38). *Youngmin Oh, Florida State University; Yiting Yao, Florida State University; Beth M. Phillips, Florida State University*
39. Narrative Comprehension and Constructions Skills Predict Longitudinal Improvements in Reading Performance among Minoritized Students (Poster 39). *Rebecca JM Gotlieb, University of California - Los Angeles; Jan Frijters, Brock University; Robin Morris, Georgia State University*
40. Navigating English Writing Instruction: Teacher Beliefs and Self-Efficacy in Caribbean Primary School Classrooms (Poster 40). *Shawna-Kaye Tucker, University of Toronto*
41. The Effect of Emotions on Digital Multimodal Reading Comprehension: Mediating Roles of Grit and Inference (Poster 41). *Jialin Li, Hong Kong Polytechnic University; Wenxin Tian, Hong Kong Polytechnic University; Siyu Zhu, The Hong Kong Polytechnic University; Qingyang Li, The Hong Kong Polytechnic University; Xinhua Zhu, Hong Kong Polytechnic University*
42. Theories in Action: Enacting Literacy Practices in Early Childhood Settings Through a Multidimensional Lens (Poster 42). *Tina Chaseley, Northern Arizona University; Victoria Damjanovic, Northern Arizona University*
43. The relationship between type of reading curriculum materials and socioeconomic status of districts (Poster 43). *Catherine Rand, West Windsor Plainsboro School District; Muriel K. Rand, New Jersey City University*
44. The TAL Framework: Interpreting Young Children's Multimodal Digital Reading Practices (Poster 44). *Amanda M. Mirabella, University of North Carolina Asheville; Ilene R. Berson, University of South Florida; Michael J. Berson, University of South Florida*
45. Exploring Critical Literacy Responses through Interactive Read-Alouds on Racial Justice and Historical Understanding (Poster 45). *Rong Zhang, Appalachian State University; Mengying Xue, University of Missouri; Xuwei Luo, Purdue University*

40.084-11. Trends and Issues in Online Teaching and

Learning. SIG-Online Teaching and Learning; Poster Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 4:15-5:45pm

Posters:

46. Assessing Early Adolescent Readiness and Growth in Online Learning with the MSRES (Poster 46). *Tracy M.*

Steele, Stanford Online High School; Diem Nguyen, Stanford University; Tomohiro Hoshi, Stanford University; Amado M. Padilla, Stanford University

47. First Impressions Matter: Emotional Primacy in Digital Learning (Poster 47). *Nicolai Benedict Plintz, University of Mannheim; Dirk Ifenthaler, University of Mannheim*
48. Rethinking Student Critical Thinking: How AI Chatbot Interactions Shape Prompting and Critical Thinking (Poster 48). *Chen Yang, The Education University of Hong Kong; Shurui Bai, The Education University of Hong Kong; Sihan Sun, The Education University of Hong Kong*
49. Social-Emotional Learning of Online Graduate Students in Education Programs: Competencies and Challenges (Poster 49). *Hyonsuk Cho, University of North Dakota; Hyun-Sook Kang, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Eunjee Jang, University of Wisconsin - River Falls*
50. Tracing Literacy-as-Events in Online Mandarin Classrooms: A New Materialist Orientation (Poster 50). *Chuan Liu, Western University; Zheng Zhang, Western University; Rachel May Heydon, University of Western Ontario*
51. Unraveling cognitive presence dynamics: An ENA of knowledge building in online discussions (Poster 51). *Eunsung Park, Tennessee Tech University; Hyangeun Ji, University of North Texas; Feliza Marie Mercado, Texas Tech University*

40.085. e-Lightning Ed-Talk Session 9 - Stage 1. AERA e-

Lightning Ed-Talks; AERA Ed Talk

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Exhibit Hall A - Stage 1; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Visual representations as resources for discussion between peers in middle school science (Stage 1, 4:20 PM). *Elon Langbeheim, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev; Einat Ben-Eliyahu, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev*

Piloting Case-Based Collaborative Learning in Secondary Health Science Classrooms: Insights from Teachers and Students (Stage 1, 4:29 PM). *Meghan Ecker-Lyster, University of Kansas; Maya Rose Watkins, University of Missouri - Kansas City; Maria Alonso Luaces, University of Kansas Medical Center; Elizabeth Ordonez, University of Kansas Medical Center; Karin Chang, University of Missouri - Kansas City*

Integrating Disciplinary Literacy Strategies into Inquiry-based Middle School Science Instruction (Stage 1, 4:38 PM). *Raju Ahmed, University of Houston; Jie Zhang, University of Houston; Sissy S. Wong, University of Houston; Laveria Hutchison, University of Houston; Samuel Katende, University of Houston*

Assessing Early Adolescent Readiness and Growth in Online Learning with the MSRES (Stage 1, 4:47 PM). *Tracy M. Steele, Stanford Online High School; Diem Nguyen, Stanford University; Tomohiro Hoshi, Stanford University; Amado M.*

Padilla, Stanford University

First Impressions Matter: Emotional Primacy in Digital Learning (Stage 1, 4:56 PM). *Nicolai Benedict Plintz, University of Mannheim; Dirk Ifenthaler, University of Mannheim*

Rethinking Student Critical Thinking: How AI Chatbot Interactions Shape Prompting and Critical Thinking (Stage 1, 5:05 PM). *Chen Yang, The Education University of Hong Kong; Shurui Bai, The Education University of Hong Kong*
Tracing Literacy-as-Events in Online Mandarin Classrooms: A New Materialist Orientation (Stage 1, 5:14 PM). *Chuan Liu, Western University; Zheng Zhang, Western University; Rachel May Heydon, University of Western Ontario*

Investigating the Impact of Title IX Sexual Harassment Policies on the K-12 Experience (Stage 1, 5:23 PM). *Megan Svajda-Hardy, Texas A&M University; John A. Williams, Texas A&M University; Quinita D. Ogletree, Texas A&M University*

Chair: *Jennifer King Rice, University of Maryland*

40.086. e-Lightning Ed-Talk Session 9 - Stage 2. AERA e-Lightning Ed-Talks; AERA Ed Talk
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Exhibit Hall A - Stage 2; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

“There’s Nothing Really There”: Meaning-Making Around the Salience of Race and Identity Among White Adolescents (Stage 2, 4:20 PM). *Tina M. Durand, Boston University; Mitali Temurnikar, Boston University; Pei Wang, Boston University*

The Nordic Myth in Education: Performing Transnational Whiteness through Other-Making (Stage 2, 4:29 PM). *Woomok Jeong, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Dugyum Kim, University of Minnesota; Younkyung Hong, Ball State University*

“Othermothering in Crisis: Women of Color Leading K-12 Schools with Care in COVID-19” (Stage 2, 4:47 PM). *Barbara Mensah, University of Alabama; Shena Sanchez, University of Alabama*

Mandarin for Whom? A Critical Review of Representation in Integrated Chinese (Stage 2, 4:56 PM). *Yuzi Gao, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*

Black Hair as Battleground: Black women educators, embodied colonization, and disembodied voyeurism (Stage 2, 5:05 PM). *Eghosa Obaizamomwan-Hamilton, Stanford University*

Analysis of women Images in Chinese State-compiled Senior High School History Textbooks (Stage 2, 5:14 PM). *Yun Zhang, East China Normal University*

Looking Back: College Students’ Recollections of Parental Academic Socialization (Stage 2, 5:23 PM). *Besjane Krasniqi, University of Maryland - Baltimore County; Susan Sonnenschein, University of Maryland - Baltimore County*

Chair: *Theodora Regina Berry, Bloomfield College of Montclair State University*

40.087. e-Lightning Ed-Talk Session 9 - Stage 3. AERA e-Lightning Ed-Talks; AERA Ed Talk
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Exhibit Hall A - Stage 3; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Immigration as Learning and Becoming: A Critical Review of Existing Literature (Stage 3, 4:29 PM). *Seda Musaoglu Aydin, Simon Fraser University; Engida Hailye Gebre, Simon Fraser University*

Expanding the Tools and Scope of Early Literacy Assessments: The Parent-based Assessment of Literate Identities (Stage 3, 4:38 PM). *Christopher Wagner, Santa Clara University*

Linguistic and cognitive predictors of listening comprehension among early elementary students (Stage 3, 4:47 PM). *Youngmin Oh, Florida State University; Yiting Yao, Florida State University; Beth M. Phillips, Florida State University*

Narrative Comprehension and Constructions Skills Predict Longitudinal Improvements in Reading Performance among Minoritized Students (Stage 3, 4:56 PM). *Rebecca JM Gotlieb, University of California - Los Angeles; Jan Frijters, Brock University; Robin Morris, Georgia State University*
Navigating English Writing Instruction: Teacher Beliefs and Self-Efficacy in Caribbean Primary School Classrooms (Stage 3, 5:05 PM). *Shawna-Kaye Tucker, University of Toronto*

The relationship between type of reading curriculum materials and socioeconomic status of districts (Stage 3, 5:14 PM). *Catherine Rand, West Windsor Plainsboro School District; Muriel K. Rand, New Jersey City University*

The TAL Framework: Interpreting Young Children’s Multimodal Digital Reading Practices (Stage 3, 5:23 PM). *Amanda M. Mirabella, University of North Carolina Asheville; Ilene R. Berson, University of South Florida; Michael J. Berson, University of South Florida*

Chair: *Sarah W. Freedman, University of California - Berkeley*

40.088. Children’s strengths for learning and communication in LOPI, in Indigenous-heritage communities of the Americas. Affiliated Groups; Structured Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 515A; 4:15-5:45pm

Participants:

Lost in Translation? Code-Switching, Hidden Curriculum, & Pitching In: How Cultural Strengths Translate (or Don’t) to Educational Settings. *Mariana Lara, California State University - Sacramento; Itzel Aceves-Azuara, California State University - Sacramento*

Helping Without Being Asked as a Cultural Strength of Latine Students: Supporting Learning in Individualistic Classrooms. *Amanda Maria Lopez, California State University, Sacramento; Itzel Aceves-Azuara, California State University - Sacramento*

Everyday Embodiments of Mutual Responsibility among

Babies and Toddlers in Tahlequah. *Jennifer Keys Adair, The University of Texas at Austin; Andrew Dayton, University of Southern California*

Change in Third-Party Attention Across Generations of Guatemalan Mayan Families. *Katie G. Silva, University of California - Santa Cruz; Itzel Aceves-Azuara, California State University - Sacramento; Barbara Rogoff, University of California - Santa Cruz*

A Pilot Study of How LOPI Supports Children's Executive Function Skills. *Lucía Alcalá, California State University - Fullerton; Suzanne Gaskins, Northeastern Illinois University*

Contributing and Participating: Increased parenting self-efficacy after parents learn elements from LOPI. *Lucretia Fairchild, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Larissa Duncan, University of Wisconsin-Madison*

Patterns of Collaboration between Indigenous and Non-Indigenous Mexican Children While Learning a Novel Computer Game. *Maricela Correa-Chavez, California State University - Long Beach; Angelica Lopez-Fraire, California State University - Dominguez Hills*

Collaboration as a Cultural Practice in Mapuche Children: Working Together Towards a Common Goal. *Paula Alonqueo, University of La Frontera*

A Model for Children's Literacy Development Inspired in LOPI. *Rebeca Mejia-Arauz, Iteso Universidad Jesuita De Guadalajara*

Chairs: *Andrew D Coppens, University of New Hampshire; Barbara Rogoff, University of California - Santa Cruz; Lucía Alcalá, California State University - Fullerton*

Discussant: *Andrew D Coppens, University of New Hampshire*

Thursday, April 9th, 5:00 pm

41.010. Indiana University Indianapolis Retirement Celebration for James "Jim" Scheurich. Affiliated Groups; Reception
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Atrium I; 5:00-7:00pm

41.011. Springer Reception. Affiliated Groups; Reception
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Plaza I; 5:00-6:00pm

Thursday, April 9th, 6:00 pm

42.010. New York University Steinhardt Community Reception. Affiliated Groups; Reception
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Wilshire Grand Ballroom I; 6:00-9:00pm

42.011. University of California, Berkeley School of Education

Reception. Affiliated Groups; Reception
Cana Rum Bar - 714 West Olympic Blvd., Los Angeles, CA 90015, Lobby; 6:00-8:00pm

Thursday, April 9th, 6:15 pm

Division Sessions

43.010. Division A Business Meeting. Division A - Administration; Business Meeting
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum C; 6:15-7:15pm

Chair: *Detra DeVerne Johnson, University of Houston*

Co-Chairs: *Kelly A. Brown, Texas A&M University - Corpus Christi; Bryan A. VanGronigen, University of Delaware*

43.011. Division E Business Meeting. Division E - Counseling and Human Development; Business Meeting
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 7; 6:15-7:15pm

Chair: *Latoya Haynes-Thoby, University of Connecticut*

43.012. Division G Business Meeting. Division G - Social Context of Education; Business Meeting
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 10; 6:15-7:15pm

Chair: *Cleveland Hayes, Indiana University - Indianapolis*

Participant: *Erica R. Davila, Lewis University*

43.013. Division H: Movers and Shakers Reception. Division H - Research, Evaluation and Assessment in Schools; Reception
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Wilshire Grand Ballroom III; 6:15-7:15pm

43.014. Division J Business Meeting and Reception. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Business Meeting
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 9; 6:15-8:15pm

Chairs: *Nolan L. Cabrera, University of Arizona; Amalia Z. Dache, University of Pennsylvania*

43.015. Division K Business Meeting. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Business Meeting
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 5; 6:15-7:15pm

Chair: *Kimberly A. White-Smith, University of San Diego*

Participants: *Nicol R. Howard, Chapman University; Erica D. McCray, University of Florida*

43.016. Division L: Educational Policy and Politics Business Meeting. Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Business Meeting
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum D; 6:15-7:15pm
Chair: *Sonya Douglass, Teachers College, Columbia University*

SIG Sessions

43.017. Action Research SIG Business Meeting. SIG-Action Research; Business Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, San Gabriel C; 6:15-7:15pm
Chair: *Catherine A. Lammert, Texas Tech University*
Participants: *Taylor Beadles, University of Texas - Permian Basin; Grace H.C. Huang, Cleveland State University; Sangeetha Carmona, California State University - Fullerton; Danielle Sutherland, Towson University*
Officers: *Monica Miller Marsh, Kent State University; Kim Lebak, Stockton University*

43.018. Adolescence and Youth Development SIG Business Meeting. SIG-Adolescence and Youth Development; Business Meeting
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 309; 6:15-7:15pm
Chair: *Marie-Anne Suizzo, University of Texas at Austin*
Officers: *Michael J. Seaberry, Clark Atlanta University; Bronwyn Nichols Lodato, Washington University in St. Louis*

43.019. Adult Literacy and Adult Education SIG Business Meeting. SIG-Adult Literacy and Adult Education; Business Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, San Fernando; 6:15-7:15pm
Chair: *Elizabeth Tighe, Georgia State University*
Co-Chairs: *Amy Pickard, Indiana University; Lindsay M. McHolme, Georgia State University*

43.020. AERA Arts & Learning SIG Business Meeting. SIG-Arts and Learning; Business Meeting
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 6; 6:15-7:15pm
Chair: *Matt Omasta, Miami University (OH)*
Participants: *Joy Gaulden Bertling, University of Tennessee; Michelle Zoss, Georgia State University; Julie Snyder, Pennsylvania State University*

43.021. Arts-Based Educational Research Business Meeting. SIG-Arts-Based Educational Research; Business Meeting
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 303B; 6:15-7:15pm

Chair: *Courtney Mauldin-Jones, Syracuse University*

43.022. Charters & School Choice SIG Business Meeting. SIG-Charters & School Choice; Business Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Santa Anita A; 6:15-7:15pm
Chair: *Charisse A. Gulosino, University of Memphis*
Officers: *Adam Kho, University of Kentucky; Chrystal S. Johnson, Purdue University*

43.023. Classroom Observation SIG Business Meeting: Envisioning the Next Generation of Classroom Observation Research. SIG-Classroom Observation; Business Meeting
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 3; 6:15-7:15pm
Chairs: *Kathleen Lynch, University of Connecticut; Bryant Jensen, Brigham Young University*
Participants: *Elizabeth L. Adams, American Institutes for Research; Flora J. Harmon, American Institutes for Research; Shifang Tang, East Texas A&M University; Rebecca O'Brien, Whitworth University; Heather C. Hill, Harvard University*

43.024. Cognition and Assessment SIG Business Meeting. SIG-Cognition and Assessment; Business Meeting
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Los Feliz; 6:15-7:15pm
Chair: *Kaiwen Man, University of Alabama*
Officer: *Jihong Zhang, University of Arkansas at Fayetteville*

43.025. SIG 17: Complexity Theories in Education Business meeting. SIG-Complexity Theories in Education; Business Meeting
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 504; 6:15-7:15pm
Chair: *Emma P. Bullock, Sam Houston State University*

43.026. Critical Muslim Education Research SIG Business Meeting. SIG-Critical Muslim Education Research; Business Meeting
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 409AB; 6:15-7:15pm
Chair: *Noor Ali, Northeastern University*

43.027. Critical Quantitative Methodologies SIG 186: Business Meeting. SIG-Critical Quantitative Methodologies; Business Meeting
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Wilshire Grand Ballroom II; 6:15-7:15pm
Chair: *Kamden Strunk, Virginia Commonwealth University*
Participants: *Christen Priddie, Indiana University; Rachel L. Renbarger, FHI 360; Mario I Suárez, Utah State University;*

Amanda J. Davis Simpfinderfer, College of William & Mary; Dan Fitzpatrick, University of Michigan; Lindy Johnson, Michigan State University

Officers: *Paulette Vincent-Ruz, New Mexico State University; Brandi N. Hinnant-Crawford, Clemson University; Yingying Jiang, Purdue University*

43.028. Disability Studies in Education (DSE) SIG Business Meeting. SIG-Disability Studies in Education; Business Meeting

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 511AB; 6:15-7:15pm

Chairs: *Kathleen M. Collins, Pennsylvania State University; Phillandra Samantha Smith, University of Pittsburgh*

Officers: *Sarah Young, Trinity Washington University; Christa S. Bialka, Villanova University; Chelsea Stinson, Binghamton University - SUNY; Arpita Sarker, University of Iowa; Isabel Mavrides-Calderon, Barnard College*

43.029. Environmental Education-SIG Business Meeting. SIG-Environmental Education; Business Meeting

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 506; 6:15-7:15pm

Chairs: *Alexandra Schindel, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Yun Wen Chan, Texas State University; Yue Li, University of Florida*

43.030. Experiential Education and Community Engagement: Scholarship and Practice (SIG #41) Business Meeting.

SIG-Experiential Education and Community Engagement: Scholarship and Practice; Business Meeting
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 2; 6:15-7:15pm

Chair: *Elaine Ramzinski, South Plains College*

43.031. Family School Community Partnership SIG Business Meeting. SIG-Family, School, Community Partnerships;

Business Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Santa Barbara A; 6:15-7:15pm

Chair: *Shana J. Haines, University of Vermont*

Officers: *Lori Delale-O'Connor, University of Pittsburgh; Judy Paulick, University of Virginia; Susana Beltran-Grimm, Portland State University; Jacqueline Lynch, Florida International University; Veronica Kang, University of Maryland; Stephany Cuevas, Chapman University; Kristin Vogel-Campbell, North Point Educational Service Center; Thomas J Capretta, The Ohio State University; Cristina C. Santamaria Graff, Indiana University - Indianapolis*

43.032. Graduate and Postdoctoral Education Across the Disciplines Special Interest Group Business Meeting.

SIG-Graduate and Postdoctoral Education across the

Disciplines; Business Meeting

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 8; 6:15-7:15pm

Chair: *Deniece Dortch, The George Washington University*

Participants: *Joshua Wallace, University of Louisville; Dana Michelle Harris, Independent Scholar; Charlotte Hayes, Florida State University; Shaoan Zhang, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Zhongxin Zheng, The George Washington University; Stephanie Lezotte, Rowan University*

43.033. Hip Hop Theories, Praxis & Pedagogies Business Meeting. SIG-Hip Hop Theories, Praxis & Pedagogies;

Business Meeting

Westin Bonaventure, Level 2, Beverly; 6:15-7:15pm

Chair: *Edmund S. Adjapong, Seton Hall University*

Co-Chair: *Stevie D. Johnson, The Ohio State University*

43.034. Creating Change: The Critical Role of New Research and Mentorship in Indigenous Studies. SIG-Indigenous

Peoples of the Pacific and Beyond; Business Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, San Gabriel B; 6:15-7:15pm

Chair: *Katrina-Ann R. Kapā'anaokalāokeola Oliveira, University of Hawai'i at Manoa*

Moderator: *Margaret J. Maaka, University of Hawai'i at Manoa; Patricia Maringi Gina Johnston-Ak, Te Whare Wananga o Awanuiarangi*

Panelists: *Kamuela M. Kimokeo, Windward Community College; Kekailoa Perry, University of Hawai'i at Mānoa; Hone Morris, Massey University; Hong Hu, Te Whare Wānanga o Awanuiārangi*

43.035. Instructional Technology SIG Business Meeting. SIG-Instructional Technology; Business Meeting

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Santa Anita B; 6:15-7:15pm

Chair: *Jill Stefaniak, University of Georgia*

Participants: *Hengtao Tang, University of South Carolina; Heather Leary, Brigham Young University; Rebecca M. Clark-Stallkamp, East Carolina University; Wei Yan, Northern Arizona University*

43.036. INTERNATIONAL STUDIES SIG Business Meeting. SIG-International Studies; Business Meeting

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304C; 6:15-7:15pm

Chair: *Keanen McKinley, College of William & Mary*

43.037. (Re)Constructing New Visions through Language: the Language and Social Processes (Un)Business Meeting. SIG-Language and Social Processes; Business Meeting

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 501B;

6:15-7:15pm

Chair: *Laura A Taylor, Rhodes College*

Speaker: *Cynthia J. Lewis, University of California - Santa Cruz*
Officers: *Faythe Beauchemin, Boston College; Lindsey W. Rowe, Clemson University; Grace Cornell Gonzales, University of Washington; Christine Seon "Sol" Rheem, Michigan State University; Min-Young Kim, University of Kansas*

43.038. Large-Scale Assessment SIG Business Meeting. SIG-Large-Scale Assessment; Business Meeting
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Echo Park; 6:15-7:15pm

Chair: *Judy H. Tang, Westat*

43.039. Law and Education SIG. SIG-Law and Education; Business Meeting
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Georgia I; 6:15-7:15pm

Chair: *Steven Michael Carlo, Monmouth University*

43.040. Longitudinal Studies Business Meeting. SIG-Longitudinal Studies; Business Meeting
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 303A; 6:15-7:15pm

Chair: *Felice J. Levine, AERA Emerita*

43.041. The Crisis in and of Marxian Educational Research and Teachers Work/Teacher Unions - SIG Business Meeting. SIG-Marxian Analysis of Society, Schools and Education Cosponsored with SIG-Teachers Work/Teacher Unions; Business Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Los Cerritos; 6:15-8:00pm

Chairs: *David Isaac Backer, Seton Hall University; Denisha Jones, Defending the Early Years*

Participants: *Brianne Kramer, Southern Utah University; Dana Morrison Simone, University of Delaware; Erin Lee Dyke, Oklahoma State University*

43.042. Mentorship & Mentoring SIG Business Meeting. SIG-Mentorship and Mentoring Practices; Business Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Level 3, Avalon; 6:15-8:00pm

Chair: *Amy Serafini, Auburn University*

43.043. Mixed Methods Research SIG Business Meeting. SIG-Mixed Methods Research; Business Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Level 3, Santa Monica A; 6:15-7:15pm

Chair: *Marcia Gail Headley, University of Delaware*

Participants: *Jen Katz-Buonincontro, Drexel University; Analay Perez, University of Michigan; Karly Ball Isaacson, Michigan State University; Rachel Saperstein McClam, Johns Hopkins University; Nathan Speer, University of Nebraska - Lincoln; Ambrosia Daphne Solis, University of*

California - Riverside

43.044. Moral Development and Education Business Meeting. SIG-Moral Development and Education; Business Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Santa Anita C; 6:15-7:15pm

Chair: *Brandy P Quinn, Louisville High School*

Co-Chair: *Heather Lawford, Bishop's University*

Moderator: *Saetbyul Kim, The University of Hong Kong*

43.045. Paulo Freire SIG Business Meeting: Celebrating twenty years. SIG-Paulo Freire; Business Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Beaudry B; 6:15-7:15pm

Chair: *Inny Accioly, Universidade Federal Fluminense*

Panelists: *Ana Lucia Cruz, STLCC - Meramec; Roseli Fischmann, Universidade de São Paulo*

43.046. Philosophical Studies in Education SIG Business Meeting. SIG-Philosophical Studies in Education; Business Meeting
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304B;

6:15-7:15pm

Chair: *Ka Ya Lee, The University of Hong Kong*

43.047. Rasch Business Meeting. SIG-Rasch Measurement; Business Meeting
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 6th Floor, Mission; 6:15-7:15pm

Chair: *Stefanie A. Wind, University of Alabama*

43.048. Religion & Education SIG Business Meeting. SIG-Religion and Education; Business Meeting
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 301A; 6:15-7:15pm

Chair: *Kevin J. Burke, University of Georgia*

43.049. Research on Evaluation SIG Business Meeting. SIG-Research on Evaluation; Business Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Santa Barbara B; 6:15-7:15pm

Chair: *Tamara V. Young, North Carolina State University*

43.050. SIG-93 Research on Learning and Instruction in Physical Education Business Meeting. SIG-Research on Learning and Instruction in Physical Education; Business Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Level 2, Echo Park; 6:15-7:15pm

Chair: *Kelly L. Simonton, University of Wyoming*

Speaker: *Ann MacPhail, University of Limerick*

Officers: *Victoria Shiver, University of New Mexico; Mara Simon, Springfield College; Seunghyun Baek, SUNY - College at Cortland; Cory Elijah Dixon, Rowan University; Emily*

Jones, Illinois State University

43.051. Research on the Superintendency SIG 97 Business Meeting. SIG-Research on the Superintendency; Business Meeting

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, La Brea; 6:15-7:15pm

Chair: *Liz Hollingworth, University of Iowa*

Officers: *Meredith L. Mountford, Florida Atlantic University; William T Holmes, Kansas State University; Rachel Sue White, University of Texas at Austin; LeAnne C. Salazar Montoya, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Sharon Ross, East Texas A&M University; James C. Coviello, St. John's University*

43.052. School Community, Climate, and Culture SIG Business Meeting. SIG-School Community, Climate, and Culture; Business Meeting

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, La Cienega; 6:15-7:15pm

Chair: *Francis H. Lim Huang, University of Missouri*

43.053. School-University-Community Collaborative Research SIG Business Meeting. SIG-School, University, Community Collaborative Research; Business Meeting

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Palos Verdes; 6:15-7:15pm

Chair: *Kathleen Provinzano, Binghamton University - SUNY*

43.054. STL SIG Business Meeting and Reception. SIG-Science Teaching and Learning; Business Meeting

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Santa Barbara C; 6:15-7:15pm

Chair: *Carla C. Johnson, North Carolina State University*

Co-Chair: *Clausell Mathis, Michigan State University*

Participants: *Shannon G. Davidson, University of Alabama; Laura Zangori, University of Missouri*

43.055. Social Emotional Learning SIG Business Meeting. SIG-Social and Emotional Learning; Business Meeting

Westin Bonaventure, Level 2, Mt. Washington; 6:15-8:00pm

Chair: *Shannon B. Wanless, University of Pittsburgh*

43.056. Sociology of Education Business Meeting and Awards. SIG-Sociology of Education; Business Meeting

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 501C; 6:15-7:15pm

Chair: *Chaddrick James-Galloway, Texas A&M University*

Speaker: *William A. Smith, University of Utah*

Officer: *Steven E. Alvarado, University of Notre Dame*

43.057. Spirituality and Education Business Meeting. SIG-Spirituality & Education; Business Meeting

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 301B; 6:15-7:15pm

Chair: *Michelle L. Tichy, Alfred University*

43.058. Stress, Coping, and Resilience SIG Business Meeting.

SIG-Stress, Coping, and Resilience; Business Meeting
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304A; 6:15-7:15pm

Chairs: *Addison Duane, Sacramento State University; Elizabeth F. Levine-Brown, George Mason University; R. Jason Lynch, Appalachian State University*

43.059. SIG189 Business Meeting: Structural Equation Modeling and Multilevel Modeling Methods. SIG-Structural Equation Modeling and Multilevel Modeling Methods; Business Meeting

InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 7th Floor, Hollywood Ballroom I; 6:15-7:15pm

Chair: *Yu-Yu Hsiao, University of New Mexico*

Co-Chair: *Yan Wang, University of Massachusetts Lowell*

Speaker: *Katherine E. Masyn, Georgia State University*

Officers: *Chi-Ning Chang, Virginia Commonwealth University; Eunsook Kim, University of South Florida; Haoran Li, University of Minnesota; Kejin Lee, Pusan National University*

43.060. SIG Studying and Self-Regulated Learning Keynote and Business Meeting. SIG-Studying and Self-Regulated Learning; Business Meeting

Westin Bonaventure, Level 3, Santa Monica B; 6:15-7:15pm

Chair: *Michelle Taub, University of Central Florida*

Co-Chair: *Aloysius C. Anyichie, Brandon University*

Officers: *Alexandra Patzak, George Mason University; Allyson A. Pitzel, University of Alabama; Melani A. Loney, Old Dominion University; Darolyn A. Flagg, Kennesaw State University*

43.061. SIG Supervision and Instructional Leadership Business Meeting. SIG-Supervision and Instructional Leadership; Business Meeting

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, San Bernardino; 6:15-7:15pm

Chair: *Megan E. Lynch, Boise State University*

Officers: *Yanira Oliveras, University of Texas - Tyler; Mary Lynne Derrington, University of Tennessee*

43.062. Survey Research in Education SIG Business Meeting.

SIG-Survey Research in Education; Business Meeting
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 6th Floor, Broadway; 6:15-7:15pm

Chair: *Jennifer Richardson McGee, Appalachian State University*

Officer: *Jeffrey R. Albrecht, University of Michigan*

43.063. Business Meeting: Test Validity Research and Evaluation SIG – 2026 AERA Annual Meeting. SIG-Test Validity Research and Evaluation; Business Meeting Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, San Gabriel A; 6:15-7:15pm

Chair: *Hao Song, Association of State and Provincial Psychology Boards*

Co-Chair: *Yi-Fang Wu, Cambium Assessment*

43.064. Vocabulary SIG Business Meeting. SIG-Vocabulary; Business Meeting Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Beaudry A; 6:15-7:15pm

Chair: *Rebecca Silverman, Stanford University*

Officers: *Emily Phillips Galloway, Vanderbilt University; Lori Bruner, University at Albany - SUNY; Christina L. Dobbs, Boston University; Elizabeth Burke Hadley, University of South Florida - Tampa; Rachel Knecht, Brigham Young University; Sabina R. Neugebauer, Temple University; Janna Brown McClain, Middle Tennessee State University; Julian Levine, University of California - Irvine*

43.065. Learning by Observing and Pitching In (LOPI): Reception and Social Gathering. Affiliated Groups; Structured Poster Session Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 515A; 6:15-7:45pm

Participants:

TikTok as a Digital Context for Examining Learning by Observing and Pitching In (LOPI). *Gloriana Lopez-Leon, University of California - Santa Cruz*

LOPI in intergenerational involvement in Filharmónica talk. *Melissa Mesinas, Whittier College*

A LOPI-ful process of new jaraneros joining community. *Yared Portillo, University of California - Berkeley*

Chairs: *Lucía Alcalá, California State University - Fullerton; Barbara Rogoff, University of California - Santa Cruz; Andrew D Coppens, University of New Hampshire*

Thursday, April 9th, 6:30 pm

44.010. USC Rossier School of Education 2026 AERA Reception. Affiliated Groups; Reception Hotel Figueroa - 939 S Figueroa Street, Los Angeles, CA 90015, Lobby; 6:30-8:30pm

Thursday, April 9th, 7:00 pm

45.010. Data Literacy and Data Science Education in K-12 Meet Up hosted by the Concord Consortium. Affiliated Groups; Reception InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 69th Floor; 7:00-

9:00pm

45.011. National Taiwan Normal University Reception 2026. Affiliated Groups; Reception Westin Bonaventure, Level 3, Emerald Bay; 7:00-9:00pm

45.012. Rutgers Graduate School of Education Reception for Alumni, Faculty, Students & Friends. Affiliated Groups; Reception Westin Bonaventure, Level 2, Rodeo; 7:00-9:00pm

Thursday, April 9th, 7:15 pm

Division Sessions

46.010. Joint Reception: Division A, Division L, University Council for Educational Administration, SAGE, Politics of Education SIG and Sociology of Education SIG. Division A - Administration Cosponsored with Division L - Educational Policies and Politics and SIG-Politics of Education, SIG-Sociology of Education; Reception JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum E; 7:15-8:45pm

Chairs: *Detra DeVerne Johnson, University of Houston; Sonya Douglass, Teachers College, Columbia University; Karl Gildner, University Council for Educational Administration*
Participant: *Nakia M. Gray-Nicolas, Queens College - CUNY*

46.011. Joint NCME/AERA-Division D Welcome Reception. Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Reception InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, Wilshire Grand Ballroom Foyer; 7:15-8:45pm

46.012. AERA Division E, G, and K Joint Reception. Division G - Social Context of Education Cosponsored with Division E - Counseling and Human Development, Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Reception JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 4; 7:15-8:45pm
Chairs: *Cleveland Hayes, Indiana University - Indianapolis; Kimberly A. White-Smith, University of San Diego; Latoya Haynes-Thoby, University of Connecticut*

SIG Sessions

46.013. Paulo Freire SIG Reception. SIG-Paulo Freire; Reception Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Beaudry B; 7:15-8:45pm

Chair: *Inny Accioly, Universidade Federal Fluminense*

46.014. Philanthropy and Education Business Meeting. SIG-Philanthropy and Education; Business Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Los Feliz; 7:15-8:15pm
Chairs: *Ida Oberman, Alanus University of Arts and Social Sciences; Laurie Beth Goodman, UMASS Global*

46.015. Stress, Coping, and Resilience Social. SIG-Stress, Coping, and Resilience; Reception
Prank Bar, 1100 South Hope Street, Los Angeles, CA, Outdoor Patio; 7:15-8:45pm
Participant: *Addison Duane, Sacramento State University*

Friday, April 10th, 7:00 am

AERA Related Activities

47.010. AERA Undergraduate Student Workshop - Day 3 (Invitation Only). AERA Related Activities; Workshop
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 505;
7:00am to 7:00pm
Chair: *George L. Wimberly, American Educational Research Association*

Committee Sessions

47.011. AERA Graduate Student Resource Center (Day 3).
Graduate Student Council; Networking Center
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 502B;
7:00am to 10:00pm

Division Sessions

47.012. Division G Rise and Shine Friday (Division G Members Only). Division G - Social Context of Education; Reception
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
7:00-7:45am

Chair: *Cleveland Hayes, Indiana University - Indianapolis*

47.013. Division I Assessment Community Meeting (Closed Meeting). Division I - Education in the Professions; Board Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Level 3, Hollywood Ballroom; 7:00-8:00am

Chairs: *Kuan Xing, University of Iowa; Brian Christopher Gin, University of Illinois at Chicago*

Participants: *Danette Waller McKinley, Foundation for*

Advancement of International Medical Education and Research; Stan Hamstra, University of Toronto; Jason Scott, AccessLex institute; Ara Tekian, University of Illinois at Chicago; Xiaomei Song, Case Western Reserve University

Friday, April 10th, 7:30 am

48.010. Breakfast Reception hosted by National Institute of Education, Nanyang Technological University, Singapore. Affiliated Groups; Reception
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Wilshire Grand Ballroom II; 7:30-11:00am

Friday, April 10th, 7:45 am

Professional Development Courses

49.010. PD26-10 Introduction to Quantitative Ethnography and Epistemic Network Analysis in the Age of AI. Professional Development and Training Committee; Professional Development Course
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Plaza I;
7:45-11:45am

Instructors: *Adaurennaya C. Onyewuenyi, The College of New Jersey; Zachari Swiecki; Andrew Ruis, University of Wisconsin*

49.011. PD26-11 Beyond the Bubble Sheet: Shaping the Future of Assessment with AI. Professional Development and Training Committee; Professional Development Course
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Plaza II;
7:45-11:45am

Directors: *Xinhui Xiong, ExamRoom AI; Mark D. Shermis, Performance Assessment Analytics, LLC*

Instructors: *Christopher Ormerod, Cambium Assessment; Xinhui Xiong, ExamRoom AI; Matthew S. Johnson, Educational Testing Service; Hong Jiao, University of Maryland; Jiawei Xiong, Curriculum Associates; Javier Suárez-Álvarez, University of Massachusetts - Amherst; Sergio Aranedo, Caveon Test Security*

49.012. PD26-12 Foundations of Learning Analytics with R. Professional Development and Training Committee; Professional Development Course
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Plaza III;
7:45-11:45am

Directors: *Jennifer K. Houchins, WestEd; Shaun B. Kellogg, North Carolina State University; Jeanne M. McClure, North Carolina State University*

Instructors: *Yang Shi, Utah State University; Rachel A. Ayieko,*

Duquesne University; Elizabeth B. Cloude, Michigan State University; Hye Rin Lee, University of Georgia; So Yeon Lee, The University of Alabama at Birmingham; Catherine A. Manly, Fairleigh Dickinson University; Son T. H. Pham, Nha Viet Institute; Francesca A. Williamson, University of Michigan; Tiffany Wright, Pepperdine University

AERA Related Activities

49.013. AERA Consortium of University and Research Institutions (AERA-CURI) and Council of Academic Deans from Research Education Institutions (CADREI) Joint Breakfast. AERA Related Activities; Reception JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 4; 7:45-9:15am

Committee Sessions

49.014. Listening, Learning, and Leading: Graduate Students in AERA. Graduate Student Council; Invited Speaker Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 402A; 7:45-9:15am

Chair: *Cammie Justus-Smith, Virginia Commonwealth University*
Panelists: *Marjorie M. Hahn, Stanford University; Edith P. Middleton, Teachers College, Columbia University; Mark Wilson, University of Houston; Benjamin Lebovitz, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Division Sessions

49.015. Education, Immigration, and (Im)mobility in a Global Context: Policy, Leadership, and Institutional Responses. Division A - Administration; Symposium
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Beaudry A; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Media (Mis)Construction of Undocumented Youth in the U.S.
Jaime Liborio Del Razo, Vassar College; Ruth María López, University of Arizona; Jaemin Josefina Lee, Harvard University

Middle Eastern Refugee Mothers in Regional Australia: Language Education and the Challenge of Integration.
Azadeh Motevali Zadeh Ardakani, Western Sydney University; Scott R. Imig, University of Newcastle

The View from the Top: Superintendents' Beliefs and Actions Regarding Their Role in the Education of Refugee Students.
Betty M. Merchant, University of Texas - San Antonio; Yesenia Ochoa, Mi Familia Vota; Christopher Flanagan-Gonzales, University of Texas - San Antonio

The Introduction of Policies, Structures and Practices to address Migration: the case of Malta. *Christopher Bezzina,*

University of Malta; Brian Vassallo, University of Malta
Leadership in times of crises: Using ICTs as tools for education in immigration contexts. The cases of New York City (USA) and Melilla (Spain). *Norma Fuentes-Mayorga, City College of New York; Marina García-Carmona, University of Granada*

Educational Policy and Leadership for Syrians under Temporary Protection: A Summary of Turkish Experience.
Deniz Örücü, Baskent University; Khalid Husny Arar, Texas State University

Chairs: *Khalid Husny Arar, Texas State University; Deniz Örücü, Baskent University*

Discussant: *Emily R. Crawford-Rossi, University of Missouri*

49.016. Division C Sylvia Scribner Award Invited Talk by Dr. Geoffrey Saxe: Understanding Learning In and Out of School: A Cultural-Developmental Approach. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Invited Speaker Session
Westin Bonaventure, Level 3, Avalon; 7:45-9:15am

Chair: *Kris D. Gutiérrez, University of California - Berkeley*

Participant: *Kris D. Gutiérrez, University of California - Berkeley*

Presenter: *Geoffrey B. Saxe, University of California - Berkeley*

49.017. Teaching and Learning with AI: Building Literacy, Agency, and Design. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Palos Verdes; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

A Framework for AI Educator Identity: Bridging Pedagogy, Disciplinary Expertise, and Emerging Technologies. *Feiwen Xiao, University of Pennsylvania; Qiuqing Li, North Carolina State University; Rebecca Ellis, The Concord Consortium; Jie Chao, The Concord Consortium; Carolyn Penstein Rose, Carnegie Mellon University; Shiyan Jiang, North Carolina State University*

AI and the Developing Child: Reimagining Social-Emotional Learning Through Interactive Media Characters. *Peixin Zhou, Harvard University; Ying Xu, Harvard University*

Factors Influencing Early Childhood Educators' Intent to Use AI-Based Technologies in a Developing Country. *Lauretta Oluwafemi Osho, Eastern New Mexico University; Oluwafemi Osho, Clemson University; Kafayat Amoke Adesina, Clemson University; Augustine Owusu Achiaw, Clemson University; Edwin Nii Bonney, Clemson University; Gertrude Arthur, University of Missouri*

Preparing Pre-Service Teachers for AI-Enhanced Teaching: A Competence Model Integrating AI Literacy, TPACK, and CoI. *Shuyu Chen, Zhejiang University; Jing Wang, Zhejiang University*

Project-Based Learning with Generative AI as Cognitive Collaborators: A DBR Approach to Higher-Order Thinking. *Kyungru Kim, Sungkyunkwan University; Dongho Kim, Seoul National University*

Chair: *Yetunde Omoyiwola Fawehinmi, Texas A&M University*

49.018. Researching Race and Ethnicity: Methods and Applications in the 20th Century. Division F - Historical Inquiry in Education; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 504;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Fundamentally Indian: The History and Development of Tribal Colleges and Universities (TCUs) 1968–1994. *Joey Shepherd, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*
The Historic Origins of Corporal Punishment and Carcerality in the American South. *Gariel Pierce, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*
Bilingual Education in a Northeastern City: Voices Over Time. *Robert Cotto, Trinity College*
Educational Aspirations in Midwestern Pakistani Immigrant Households. 1965-1999. *Itrat Sultan, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*
“Carpeting the Summer”: West Side and Central City Schools in Salt Lake City. *Callie Avondet, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Chair: *Jennifer Johnson, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Discussant: *Jennifer Johnson, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

49.019. It Was Never Just About the Grant: The Before, During, and Afters of Educational Justice Work in Times of Grant Cancellation. Division G - Social Context of Education; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 403A;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Struggles for Black Space and Specificity in Public Education. *Brandee M. Otis, Northwestern; kihana miraya ross, Northwestern University*
Building Better Together: Reclaiming Community Partnerships in STEM for Black Youth. *Arikpo Ekaette Dada, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*
Exploring Black Evanstonian Visions of STEM Education in a Shifting Political Landscape. *Shai Moore, Northwestern University*
University Policy Shifts and Equity Strategy Adaptation in STEM Programs within Diverse Ecosystems. *Sydney Grae Simmons, Northwestern University*
What It Means to Continue the Work: Relationships and Community That Persist Beyond Grant-Cancellation. *Brandee M. Otis, Northwestern; Arikpo Ekaette Dada, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Shai Moore, Northwestern University; Sydney Grae Simmons, Northwestern University; Sepehr Vakil, Northwestern University; kihana miraya ross, Northwestern University; Nichole D. Pinkard, Northwestern University*

Chair: *Sepehr Vakil, Northwestern University*

Discussant: *Brandee M. Otis, Northwestern*

49.020. Refusing Limitation, Protecting Public Education: Researchers and Practitioners Responding Together to K12 DEI Attacks. Division G - Social Context of Education; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 301A;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Caricature and Crush: A Conflict Campaign and Limitation Effect Reducing Opportunity in the Nation’s Schools. *Mica Pollock, University of California - San Diego*
Messaging to Protect Immigrant and LGBTQ Student Access to/Learning in Schools in an Attack Era. *Hirokazu Yoshikawa, New York University; Sophia Rodriguez, New York University*
Public Learning for a Multiracial Democracy: The Research on What We Stand to Lose under Education Gag Orders. *Janelle T. Scott, University of California - Berkeley; Amy Stuart Wells, Bank Street College of Education*
Culture Wars, Curriculum Battles & Public Schools: Pursuing a Bottom-Up Education Policy Research Agenda for the Field. *Danfeng Soto-Vigil Koon, University of San Francisco; Huriya Jabbar, University of Southern California; Joseph J. Ferrare, University of Washington Bothell*
Considering Needed Efforts through the Lens of State Efforts to Sustain and Grow Education Opportunity. *Heather Fleming, University of Missouri - St. Louis; Lisa Vahey, Honesty for Ohio Education*

Chair: *Mica Pollock, University of California - San Diego*

Discussant: *Janelle T. Scott, University of California - Berkeley*

49.021. “Looking Back, Looking Forward:” Envisioning Asian Diasporas as Methodologies for “Thriving Futures”. Division G - Social Context of Education; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 406AB;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Defying Exclusion, Disposability, and Dehumanization: A Critical Historiography of Asian Diaspora Experiences in the U. S. *Suniti Sharma, Saint Joseph's University*
Chinese Diasporas as Methodologies: Grieving against Empires, Grieving toward Justice. *Lin Wu, Western Oregon University*
Humanizing Research with Asian American Youth and Families: Centering Intergenerational Diasporic Experiences. *Min Yu, Wayne State University; Roland Sintos Coloma, Wayne State University; Wenyang Sun, University of Utah; Jungmin Kwon, Michigan State University; Pyeongeun Kim, Michigan State University; Seungwoo Hwang, Michigan State University*
Re-Storying and Remembering Place: Kanaka Ōiwi (Native Hawaiian) and Asian Diaspora Ancestral Knowledge as

Methodologies. *Kourtney Kawano, University of California - Berkeley*

Fugitive Ways of Knowing and Desires for Living: UndocuAsian Diasporas as Methodologies. *Siyue Lena Wang, University of California - Los Angeles*

Asian Diaspora "Storywork". *Ming Fang He, Georgia Southern University*

Chair: *Ming Fang He, Georgia Southern University*

Discussant: *Roland Sintos Coloma, Wayne State University*

49.022. Understanding Disparities and Imagining Justice:

Explorations Across the Professions. Division I - Education in the Professions; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 3; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Doctoral Engineering Students' Sexual Harassment Experiences and Sexual Harassment Climate Perceptions.

Nicole M. Else-Quest, University of California - Los Angeles; Julie Aldridge, The Ohio State University; So Yoon Yoon, University of Cincinnati

National Study of Milestone Evaluation Differences by Gender and Race in Anesthesiology Residency Training. *Ting Sun, University of Utah; Yoon Soo Park, University of Illinois at Chicago; Fei Chen, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Nikki Wilkinson, University of Illinois at Chicago; Pedro Tanaka, Stanford University*

Anti-Black Racism in the History of Canadian Physiotherapy Education. *Oyin Otubusen, University of Manitoba*

When Identity Matters: Physician Race, Gender, and Group Membership in Implicit and Explicit Bias. *Lynn Foster-Johnson, Dartmouth College*

Who Chooses Nursing? Similarities and Differences in Pre-college Characteristics of Filipina/x/o Americans Nursing Majors versus Their Non-nursing Peers. *Elaine Jessica Castillo Tamargo, California State University - Long Beach*

Chair: *Ulana A. Luciw-Dubas, National Board of Medical Examiners*

Discussant: *Gareth Gingell, Dell Medical School*

49.023. Conditions for Change: Organizational Accountability, Reform, and Commitment in Higher Ed.

Division J - Postsecondary Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum H; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Qualitative Analysis on Developmental Education Reform Act (DERA) Implementation at Illinois Community Colleges.

Hanna Kim, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Hannah M. Kuneyl, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Yasamin Khoshpour, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Lorenzo D. Baber, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign

Volunteering, Service-Learning, and Civic Engagement at

Community Colleges: A Typology of College Practice. *Carol Cutler White, Mississippi State University; Janet L. Johnson, Edstar Analytics, Inc.; Stephanie B. King, Mississippi State University*

The Power Dynamics of Philanthropic Foundations: How They Fund Minority-Serving Institutions. *Nabih Haddad, Michigan State University*

"I Need More Agency To Do This Work:" The Organizational Commitments Necessary for Equity-Oriented Change. *Eric R. Felix, San Diego State University; Angel D. Gonzalez, California State University - Fresno; Leslie Gomez, San Diego State University*

Chair: *Steve Desir, University of Southern California*

Discussant: *Michael Lanford, University of North Georgia*

49.024. Faculty Innovations at Minority Serving Institutions.

Division J - Postsecondary Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum I; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Collaborative, Open-Source Projects as Innovative Work-Based Learning Opportunities for Underserved Computer Science Students. *Elizabeth Apple-Meza, University of Washington; Colleen Pawlicki, Troy Street Services; Kendrick Hang, Washington State Board for Community & Technical Colleges; Tyler Schrock, Green River College; Tyler Menezes, CodeDay; Kevin Wang, Mentors in Tech*

Empowering Faculty as Leaders of Equity-Driven Change in Higher Education. *Shujin Zhong, University of North Florida; Nicole Marie-Gerardi MacCalla, University of California - Los Angeles; Cynthia Joseph, University of California-Los Angeles (UCLA) - Los Angeles, CA; Dawn Purnell, University of California - Los Angeles*

"It Really Felt Like They Cared": How learning communities serve a Hispanic Serving Institution. *Tara Schwitzman-Gerst, Kean University; Liza Ann Bolitzer, Kean University; Peter Bardys, Kean University*

Unforgetting Histories and Imagining Futures: Experiences of Latinx Faculty in Tenure-Track Appointments at Hispanic-Serving Institutions. *Carlos A Galan, California State University - San Bernardino*

Chair: *Deborah Loewenberg Ball, University of Michigan*

Discussant: *Valeria G. Dominguez, University of California - Los Angeles*

49.025. STEM Education Pathways for Student Success.

Division J - Postsecondary Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum F; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Gendered Transition from STEM Education to Workforce: Access Does Not Guarantee Success. *Juyoung Kim, University of Georgia; Yunhee Jung, Catholic Kwandong University*

Sending (Mixed) Signals: Comparing Computing Terminology in MSI Graduate Programs and Job Markets Across Regions. *Bret Staudt Willet, Florida State University; Annie M. Wofford, Florida State University; Charlotte Hayes, Florida State University; Lara Perez-Felkner, Florida State University*

Navigating STEM Pathways: Two-Year College Student's Persistence in STEM After Completing an Introductory Calculus Course. *Talia Kessler, Georgia State University; Jennifer R. Esposito, Georgia State University*

Intersecting Identities and Capital Resources: Predicting STEM Major Choice Among Women and First-Generation College Students. *Xinting Wu, Florida State University; Lara Perez-Felkner, Florida State University*

Discussant: *Sarah Rodriguez, Virginia Tech*

49.026. Teaching, Learning, and Pedagogy. Division J -

Postsecondary Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum G; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

"Dealing with these situations": Teaching Undergraduates Professional Ethics by Reflecting on Bias. *Sarah A Burcher, University of Alabama; Makayla Lucas, University of Alabama; Kate O'Rourke, University of Alabama; Isabella Martin, University of Alabama; Kimberly Tomeny, University of Alabama*

From Risk to Resilience: Mapping Teacher Candidates' Academic Challenges and Resilience. *Donghyun Kang, Tennessee State University; UrLeaka W. Newsome, Tennessee State University; Lou Anne Wilkes, Tennessee State University; Kisha C. Bryan, Tennessee State University*

Tracing Changes in Student Perceptions of Effective Post-Secondary Teaching Before, During, and After COVID-19. *Hyecheon Lee, Georgia Institute of Technology; Amanda L. Nolen, Georgia Institute of Technology; Laura Carruth, Georgia Institute of Technology*

Burnout and Psychological Distress Across U.S. Postgraduate Trainees, Fellows, and Students: A Comprehensive Meta-Analysis. *Mohammad Jahanaray, Virginia Commonwealth University; Atena Pasha, University of South Carolina; Ali Jahanaray, Clemson University*

Experiences of Mathematics Majors in Multilingual Proof-Writing Sessions. *Jeffrey Pair, California State University - Long Beach; Sabrina Kramer, California State University - Long Beach*

Discussant: *Lois Calian Trautvetter, Northwestern University*

49.027. Beyond Acknowledgement: Decolonial Futures in Education and Disability Studies. Division K - Teaching

and Teacher Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 8; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

The Stubborn Erasure of Indigenous Sovereignty and Disability in Teacher Education. *Samantha Marie Jacob, University of Wisconsin-Madison; Gardner R Seawright, University of Wisconsin - Whitewater*

Land Acknowledgment in Action: Dedicated Study of Indigeneity in an Elementary Teacher Education Program. *Saba Khan Vlach, University of Iowa; Lia Plakans, University of Texas at Austin; EunJung Kim, University of Iowa; I-Chun Hsiao, University of Iowa*

"It Opened my Mind and Heart": Toward a Humanizing Professional Development Framework For Anti-Colonial Futures. *Christine Stanton, Montana State University; Jordann Lankford, Great Falls Public Schools; Roxann Smith, Fort Peck Community College*

Justice-Oriented Math Pedagogies in Politically Restrictive Times. *Taryrn T.C. Brown, University of Florida; Hyunyi Jung, Texas A&M University*

Chair: *Elizabeth Holliday Morgan, Morgan State University*

Discussant: *Blanca Gabriela Caldas Chumbes, University of Minnesota*

49.028. Empowering Educators for Equitable & Integrated Computer Science Learning: Innovations in PD. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 1; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

An Examination of K-8 Educator Discourse Surrounding Student Competence in a Computer Science Professional Learning Context. *Amy Maples, University of Tennessee; Chulin Chen, University of Tennessee; Lynn L. Hodge, University of Tennessee*

Empowering Teachers as Leaders: A Professional Learning Model for Computational Thinking Integration. *Robin Jocius, University of Kentucky; Melanie Blanton, Texas Tech University; Candace Joswick, University of Texas - Arlington; Jennifer Albert, The Citadel; Ian O'Byrne, College of Charleston; Deepti Joshi, The Citadel*

Implementing an Accelerated Computer Science Teacher Summer Bootcamp in a Southeastern State. *Marvin Evans, Coastal Carolina University; Alex Fegely, Coastal Carolina University; Kingfeiyue Liu, The Ohio State University; Crystal Cox, Coastal Carolina University*

Navigating Future Preschool Classrooms: Exploring Self-efficacy and Outcomes Expectations for Technology-Integrated Education. *Jana Patricia Millonado Valdez, Education University of Hong Kong; Jet Uy Buenconsejo, The Education University of Hong Kong; Weipeng Yang, The Education University of Hong Kong; Xunyi Lin, Fujian Normal University; Anika Saxena, The Education University of Hong Kong; Jesus Alfonso Daep Datu, The University of Hong Kong*

Unforgetting exclusion: Humanizing computer science pedagogy through equity-focused professional learning

community. *Minsun Shin, Montclair State University; Katherine Herbert, Montclair State University; Sumi Hagiwara, Montclair State University*

Discussant: *Abby C. Emerson, Touro University*

49.029. Global Perspectives on Preparation for Diversity: Enacting Anti-Bias Pedagogies for Transformative Multicultural Education. Division K - Teaching and

Teacher Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 9; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Envisioning, Exploring, and Enacting Anti-Bias Pedagogies in ELA Teacher Education. *Jennifer Ervin, University of Wisconsin - Eau Claire*

Experiences of Multicultural Education from the Perspective of Preservice Teachers. *Jaebum Han, Kangwon National University; Hyojeong Kim, Kangnam University*

Preparing Teacher Candidates for Culturally and Linguistically Diverse Classrooms in Turkiye: Challenges and Opportunities. *Ozge Yalciner, University of Kentucky*

“A Wealth of Knowledge”: Designing Courses That Transform How Educators See Students—and Themselves. *Sarah Anne Eckert, Eastern University; Miriam Marguerita Gomez Witmer, Millersville University of Pennsylvania; Jill May Swavely, Temple University; Luca Poxon, Temple University; Michelle J. Sobolak, University of Pittsburgh; Beth R. Sockman, East Stroudsburg University of Pennsylvania*

Chair: *Saroja Warner, Wested*

Discussant: *Gabriela López, Stanford University*

49.030. Innovations and Advances in Mathematics Instruction.

Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Structured Poster Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 515A; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

1. Doing the Math with Paraeducators: Enhancing and Expanding a PreK-3 Math Professional Development Model (Poster 1). *Audrey E. Martinez-Gudapakkam; Karen Mutch-Jones, TERC; Brandon Sorge, Indiana University Indianapolis; Judy Storeygard, TERC; Sabrina De Los Santos Rodríguez, TERC; Sarah Hill, TERC; Connie Henry, Boston Public Schools; Thomas Schindler, Purdue University; Gina Borgioli Yoder, Indiana University; Lynette Osborne, National Academy of Engineering; Elizabeth Osche, PERG Learning*

2. Examining Geometry Teachers’ Changes to Design-based Lessons for Engaging Students in Math Modelling (Poster 2). *Saadeddine S. Shehab, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Gloriana Gonzalez, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Edward Powers, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

3. Exploring Emergent Bilinguals’ Positioning in Translanguaging-Oriented Math Instruction (Poster 3). *Jiyeong Joann Yi, Iowa State University; Jasmine Sourwine, Iowa State University; Shristi Shrestha, Iowa State University*

4. Integrating Children’s Experiences and Mathematical Learning: Using Addition to Explore Dynamic Family Structures (Poster 4). *José Martínez Hinestroza, University of Texas - San Antonio*

5. “It takes courage to come out and be vulnerable:” Coaching for Social Justice Mathematics (Poster 5). *Kari Kokka, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Michelle Cody, University of California, Davis*

6. Mentoring for Responsive Teaching: Characterizing Mentoring Practice of Collaborative Pedagogical Reasoning (Poster 6). *Janine Remillard, University of Pennsylvania; Annabel Stoler, Boston University; Riku Sayuj, University of Pennsylvania; Arati Bapat, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Anna Dailey, Boston University; Carol Vieira, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Sophie Meuch, University of Pennsylvania; Mary Klehr, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Hala N. Ghouseini, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Meghan Shaughnessy, Boston University*

7. Understanding How Mathematics Teachers Take Up Instructional Nudges (Poster 7). *Zandra de Araujo, University of Florida; Amber Grace Candela, University of Missouri - St. Louis; Samuel Otten, University of Missouri*

8. Understanding the Role of Rehearsals in Mathematics Language Routine Studio (Poster 8). *Sarah Ann Roberts, University of California - Santa Barbara; Royce Olarte, University of California - Santa Barbara; Evelyn Margarita Vera-Flandez, University of California - Santa Barbara; Hyejeon Han, University of California - Santa Barbara; Grace Rincon Garcia, University of California - Santa Barbara; Vincent Robinson, University of California - Santa Barbara; Mandy Kong, University of California - Santa Barbara*

Chair: *Ilana S. Horn, Vanderbilt University*

Discussant: *Ilana S. Horn, Vanderbilt University*

49.031. Resisting Oppression and Navigating Policy in Education. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 6; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Critical Race Coaching: Centering Racial Realism to Sustain Antiracism in Schools. *Benjamin Blaisdell, East Carolina University*

Confronting “Divisive Concepts” Legislation: Educators’ Principled Resistance to Florida HB 7. *Yiting Chu, University of South Florida - Tampa*

Connecting the Dots: How One Teacher Navigates High-Stakes

Testing While Cultivating Civic Engagement. *Christopher Irwin, Florida International University; Darryl Dickerson, Florida International University; Nicholas Oehm, Florida International University; Joshua Alexander Ellis, Louisiana State University*

Creating Sustainable Sanctuaries: A Collective Liberation Approach to Developing Fugitive Spaces for Educational Communities. *Pete Locher, American University; Yasmin Elgoharry, University of Connecticut; Elise Robison, Howard University*

Teaching Against the Grain: Disrupting the Anti-Black Logics of Schooling. *Jaleel R. Howard, University of California - Riverside*

Discussant: *Tianna Dowie-Chin, University of Georgia*

49.032. Transnational Journeys: Identity, Power, and Commitment in Teaching. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 7; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Emotion, Identity, and Institutional Power: A longitudinal Narrative Inquiry into Novice Teacher Experience Abroad. *Yijing Wang, The University of Auckland; Christine Biebricher, Auckland University; Lawrence Jun Zhang, University of Auckland*

Long-Term Influence of Short-Term Study Abroad: Critical Incidents that Informed Teachers' Professional Trajectories. *Jeremy Hilburn, University of North Carolina - Wilmington; Brad M. Maguth, University of Akron; William Visco, University of Akron*

Negotiating Music Teacher Identity in China: Capital, Structure, and Career Divergence. *NUO HAN, 北京师范大学*

Promoting Teachers' Intercultural Citizenship through an ELF-context International Service-learning Program between Taiwan and Indonesia. *Dale Leonard Albanese, National Sun Yat-sen University; Yu-Hui Chang, National Sun Yat-sen University; Shih-An Yang, National Sun Yat-sen University*

Chair: *Jeremy Hilburn, University of North Carolina - Wilmington*

49.033. Teachers on the Move: Recruitment, Retention, and Attrition in Context. Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 10; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Student and Institutional Characteristics That Predict Progression Across the University-Based Teacher Pipeline. *Jae Eun Choi, University of Michigan; Matthew Ronfeldt, University of Michigan*

Teacher attrition amid geographical, societal, and economic realities: Fifteen years of the Kansas teacher workforce.

Chanh Bao Lam, Kansas State University

Teacher Turnover in the U.S.: Who Moves, Who Leaves, and Why? *Tiffany S. Tan, Learning Policy Institute; Wesley Wei, Learning Policy Institute; Emma García, Learning Policy Institute; Desiree Carver-Thomas, Learning Policy Institute*

Revisiting The Rural Teacher Workforce: Insights from a Novel Rurality Measure. *Yujia Liu, University of Missouri; Chanh Bao Lam, Kansas State University; J. Cameron Anglum, Lehigh University; J.R. Funk, University of Missouri; Tuan D Nguyen, University of Missouri*

Transitioning Teacher Talent: An Ethnoracial Descriptive Portrait of the Paraprofessional-to-Teacher Pipeline in NYC Public Schools. *Luis A Rodriguez, New York University; Xinghua Toby Wu, New York University; Emily Myers, New York University*

Chair: *Sherry L. Deckman, CUNY, Lehman College and Graduate Center*

Discussant: *Susan Kemper Patrick, Learning Policy Institute*

SIG Sessions

49.034. Critical Approaches to Teacher Development in Arts Education. SIG-Arts and Learning; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 2; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Approaching Critical Reflective Practice in Art Teacher Education. *Sarah T. Travis, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Integrating Animatronics and Makerspace Technologies for Culturally Responsive Teaching in Teacher Preparation. *Mousumi De, University of Redlands; Iyan Barrera-Sandri, University of Redlands*

"Yeah, That's Not Okay": What Teaching Stories Tell Us About Early Career Dance & Theatre Teachers. *Betsy Maloney Leaf, University of Minnesota; Emily Jane Wall Burnley, University of Minnesota*

The Effectiveness of Drama-based Read Alouds: How Teacher Instructional Strategies Relate to Student Narrative Recall. *Scott C. Marley, Arizona State University; Lauren van Huisstede, Arizona State University; Sepide Pazhouhi, Arizona State University; Katie Bernstein, Arizona State University; M. Adelaida Restrepo, University of South Florida; Erin Rotheram-Fuller, Arizona State University; Jenny Millinger, Childsplay Theatre Company; Michael F. Kelley, Arizona State University; Melissa Pierce-Rivera, Midwestern University*

Becoming a dance teacher: Chinese dance student teachers' perceptions of their student teaching experience. *lilin chen, Beijing Normal University*

Chair: *Kristen Schaffer, Mount Royal University*

Discussant: *lilin chen, Beijing Normal University*

49.035. Arts based educational research and imagining

future(s). SIG-Arts-Based Educational Research; Paper Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304C; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Imagining Trans-Affirming Futures: Creative Visions from TNB Students and Caregivers. *SJ Hemmerich, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Imagining Futures by Unforgetting Histories: Participatory Filmmaking with Refugee Youth. *Melissa Hauber-Özer, University of Missouri; Kelly Leavitt, University of Missouri; Viviana Goelkel, University of Missouri*

Education, Incarceration, Improvisation: Youth Self-Concept on the School-to-Prison Pipeline. *Kelly Lynn Brady, CUNY - Graduate Center*

Rehearsals for change: Exploring how arts-based educational research fosters equitable and inclusive classrooms. *Mindy Roberta Carter, McGill University; Sabi Hinkson, McGill*

Chair: *Khalilah Odessa Ali, Spelman College*

Discussant: *Maggie Broderick, National University*

49.036. Latin America Writes Back: Praxiologies in Language

Education. SIG-Bilingual Education Research; Symposium

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304A;

7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Breaking Silences: Poetic Reflections on Liberation in the Brazilian American Classroom. *Karina O. De Paula, Texas Tech University*

Ideological Clarity for English Language Teachers in Paraguay. *Valentina Canese, Universidad Nacional de Asunción; Christian J. Faltis, Texas A&M International University*

We don't need another hero: valuing ongoing local praxiologies in the Teaching of English to (Very) Young Learners in Brazil. *Juliana Tonelli, Universidade Estadual de Londrina; Alex Alves Egido, Federal University of Maranhão*

Chair: *Karina O. De Paula, Texas Tech University*

Discussant: *Zhongfeng Tian, Rutgers University - Newark*

49.037. Reimagining Education: From Colonial Control to Transnational Mobility. SIG-Caribbean and African

Studies in Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum J; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Caribbean Educational Policy Alignment: Small and Large Population Country Comparison. *Jade Pratt, Pepperdine University*

Curriculum as Control: Moral Governance, Mistranslation, and the Surveillance of Afro-Jamaicans, 1830–1880. *Faith D. Northern, New York University*

Reconceptualizing Transnationalism: Black Global Mobility, Literacies, and Social Class. *Lakeya Afolalu, University of*

Washington; Allison Skerrett, University of Texas at Austin
Sense of Belonging Among Caribbean Students in Dutch Higher Education. *Kennedy Aquilino Tielman, Fontys University of Applied Sciences; Yucata Lienga, Fontys University of Applied Science; Karin Verouden, Fontys University of Applied Science*

Chair: *Carmel Geneva Roofe, University of the West Indies - Mona Campus*

Discussant: *Danielle Charlemagne, University of Georgia*

49.038. Reclaiming Selves, Histories, Language, and Culture Through Relational Processes of (Re)membering. SIG-

Critical Educators for Social Justice; Symposium

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 301B; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Sib Hlub Sib Txhawb: A Methodology for HMoob In-relations Mentoring. *Vicky C. Xiong-Lor, California State University - Fresno; Kaozong Nancy Mouavangsou, University of Wisconsin - Eau Claire; Jenna Cushing-Leubner, University of Wisconsin - Whitewater*

Freedom Dreamers: Voices from Southeast Asian American Educators. *Nga-Wing Anjela Wong; Choua P. Xiong, University of Wisconsin - Oshkosh*

HMoob Sonic World Making and Refusal through Cassette Tapes. *Caroline Thao, Twin Rivers United School District*
Ancestral Memories: Lug Ntsuag as a Methodology of Healing. *Karen Vang, University of California - Davis*

“I Ain’t Tryin’ to Curse Us”: Remembering Hmong Language and Culture with Youth. *Pa Nou Vue, University of California - Berkeley*

Discussant: *Ezekiel Joubert, California State University - Los Angeles*

49.039. Critical Race Theory and Epistemic Mechanisms. SIG-Critical Examination of Race, Ethnicity, Class and Gender in

Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum C; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Critical Race Theory as Lineage Work. *Antar A. Tichavakunda, University of California - Santa Barbara*

Racial Microaffirmations: Assessing the Field for Research on Affirmations and Healing for People of Color in Education. *Lindsay Pérez Huber, California State University - Long Beach; Daniel Gilbert Solorzano, University of California - Los Angeles*

Critical Race Mentoring: A Framework for Supporting Men of Color. *Eligio Martinez, Cal Poly Pomona; Derrick R. Brooms, Morehouse College; Joseph Romero-Reyes, Iowa State University; Joe Louis Hernandez, Mt. San Antonio College*

QuantCrit School-Level Equity Index: Mapping Educational Redlining. *Sojung Park, University at Albany - SUNY;*

Nicholas S. Bell, University of Connecticut

Honoring Collective Intergenerational Educational Experiences of Latinas through Pláticas-Testimonios. *Adrianna González Ybarra, The University of Texas Rio Grande Valley; Stephanie Hernandez Rivera, Elon University*

Chair: *Rossina Zamora Liu, University of Maryland*

49.040. Centering Children's Literature as a Transformative Tool for Imagining Futures in Early Childhood Education. SIG-Critical Perspectives on Early Childhood Education; Paper Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 303A; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

A Critical Analysis of Gun Violence Portrayed in Picturebooks. *Yafen Lo, California State University - Los Angeles; Su-Jeong Wee, California State University - Los Angeles; Mengying Xue, University of Missouri; Qiong Wu, California State University - Los Angeles*

Deportation, Race, and Representation: A Critical Content Analysis of Latinx Families in Children's Picturebooks. *Mariana Lizeth Gomez Becerra, University of California - Irvine; Claudia Kouyoumdjian, California State University - Los Angeles; Su-Jeong Wee, California State University - Los Angeles; Yafen Lo, California State University - Los Angeles*

Interactive Read Alouds as Culturally Sustaining Trajectories to Imagine Futures for All Children. *Laura Marcela Cardona Berrio, Texas A&M University - Corpus Christi*

Language, Literacy, Liberation: Oral Storytelling and Pluralistic Picture Books as Decolonial Tools. *Aura Yarenis Perez-Gonzalez, California State University - Long Beach; Ayesha Rabi-Raol, Sonoma State University*

Unforgetting Abuelitas: Examining the Depiction of Latinx Characters in Children's Picture Books. *Jessica Cooper, Pre-K 4 SA; Maria G. Leija, University of Texas - San Antonio; Rica Ramirez, University of Texas - San Antonio*

Chair: *Eboni N. Bango, Texas A&M University*

Discussant: *Brita A. Bookser, Santa Clara University*

49.041. Culturally Sustaining Early Literacy Pedagogies and Our Futures: Dynamic Stories and Practices from PK-6 Communities. SIG-Critical Perspectives on Early Childhood Education; Symposium

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 303B; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Culturally Sustaining Early Literacy Pedagogies and Our Futures. *Sandra Lucia Osorio, Erikson Institute; Sakeena Everett, University of Connecticut; Kindel Turner Nash, Appalachian State University; Shanah H. Fitts, Appalachian State University; Bilal Polson, Northern Parkway School; Greg McClure, Appalachian State University*

Sustaining Religious Literacies in Authoritarian Eras: Re-

membering Humanity in Early Childhood Classrooms.

Serena Wilcox, Wayne State University; Assadullah Sadiq, California State University - Channel Islands; Nora Peterman, University of Missouri - Kansas City; Ekaterina Strelakova-Hughes, University of Missouri - Kansas City
Poetic Play for Sustaining Chinese Linguistic and Cultural Heritage. *Yixuan Wang, Gwinnett County Public Schools*
But Wait, There's More! Exploring Counternarratives in a 5th Grade Black History Unit. *Mia Hicks, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Tracey Bullington, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Emily Machado, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Kristin Pellerin, Madison Metropolitan School District; Carly McClennahan, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

From the Mouths of Mothers: Black Language Advocacy and Early Literacy Justice. *Teaira C. McMurtry, University of Alabama - Birmingham*

Culturally Sustaining Care and Education through Loose Parts Play with Natural Desert Materials. *Rhianna K. Thomas, New Mexico State University; Leanna Lucero, New Mexico State University; Adriana V Cardenas, New Mexico State University; Rubi Orozco, La Semilla Food Center; Abeer Al-Ghawi, Ngage New Mexico; Christina Ruybal, NMSU School for Young Children; Abigail Wisniewski, NMSU School for Young Children; Olga Grays, Ms. Olga's Daycare*

Chair: *Darius Phelps, New York University*

Discussant: *Mariana Souto-Manning, Erikson Institute*

49.042. Intersectional Pathways: BIPOC Resistance and Repair in Academic Spaces. SIG-Disability Studies in Education; Paper Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 511AB; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Challenging Normativity: Mapping the Intersectional Performativity of Blackness and Disability in Higher Education. *Prilly Bicknell-Hersco, York University*
The Call is Coming from Inside the House: Racism and Ableism in US Medical Education. *Hannah L. Kakara Anderson, Maastricht University; Abigail W. Konopasky, Dartmouth College; Justin Bullock, University of Washington; Lisa Meeks, University of Illinois College of Medicine; Neera R. Jain, The University of Auckland*
Counter-Storytelling: Qualitative process of Mind and Heart. *Whitney S. Hanley, University of Kentucky; David I. Hernandez-Saca, University of Northern Iowa; Shariese Katrell-Abdullah, Mercer County Community College*
Reparative and Anti-Eugenic Futures: A University Case Study. *Lauren Shallish, Rutgers University - Newark*
They (Won't) Erase Us: The Criminalization and Resistance of Disabled Black American Activists in Education. *Da'Shay P. Templeton, California Lutheran University; Ta'lia Gordon, University of South Carolina*

Chair: *Saili S. Kulkarni, San Jose State University*
Discussant: *Cassandra Victoria Guzman, Cornell University*

49.043. Foundations for Lasting Equity and Transformation:

Policy, Organization, and Professional Practice. SIG-

Educational Change; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum
D; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Educational Change Through Land-Based Learning: Local
Indigenous Knowledge and Teacher Professional
Development. *Bonny Lynn Donovan, University of British
Columbia - Okanagan; Leyton Schnellert, University of
British Columbia; Sarah Buffett, Cornell University,
University of British Columbia; Sara Florence Davidson,
Simon Fraser University*

Faculty Cluster Hiring as a Catalyst for Racial Equity in
Academic Departments. *Román Liera, Montclair State
University; Rosa M. Acevedo, University of Pittsburgh; Baili
Park, University of Pittsburgh; Aireale J. Rodgers,
University of Wisconsin - Madison; Heather N. McCambly,
University of Pittsburgh*

Middle Leaders and the Illusion of Reform: Unpacking Faux
Comprehension and Pseudo-Understanding in Curriculum
Change. *Chun Sing Maxwell Ho, The Education University
of Hong Kong; Chiu Kit Lucas Liu, The Education
University of Hong Kong*

Sustaining Change: Inquiry-Driven Innovations that Persevere.
*Ellen B. Meier, Teachers College, Columbia University;
Madalina Ciocanu, Teachers College, Columbia University;
Jessica Yusaitis Pike, Teachers College, Columbia
University; Caron M. Mineo, Teachers College, Columbia
University; Karen Kirsch Page, Teachers College, Columbia
University; Yingxin Ye, Teachers College, Columbia
University*

Chair: *Román Liera, Montclair State University*

Discussant: *Jennie Weiner, University of Connecticut*

**49.044. The Education Leaders We Need Now: Innovations in
Leadership Development and Approaches to Leading.**

SIG-Leadership for School Improvement; Paper Session

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Los Cerritos; 7:45-
9:15am

Participants:

Empowering Teacher Leadership: Professional Development
for Teachers and School Leaders Based on Empirical Data.
*Joanne Connor, Rowan University; Margaret Thornton,
Rowan University*

GEAR UP for Change: Reimagining Administrators as
Instructional Leaders. *Charlotte Rainey Parham, University
of Central Arkansas; Donna Wake, University of Central
Arkansas*

Leadership Style and Innovation: Autonomy Satisfaction,
Frustration, and Innovativeness as Mediating Pathways.

*Lindsey Devers Basileo, Instructional Empowerment;
Merewyn E. Lyons, Instructional Empowerment; Michael
David Toth, Instructional Empowerment; Barbara Otto,
Diaconia University of Applied Sciences; Franz Hofmann,
University of Salzburg*

Leading for Sustainability Education in Complex Times:

Theorizing Leadership within a Networked Learning
System. *Romina Madrid Miranda, University of Stirling;
Elizabeth Rushton, University of Stirling; Letizia Riddell,
University of Stirling*

Leading Professional Learning Networks of Future-Ready
School Leaders in Hong Kong: Expert Principals'
Perspective. *Jiafang Lu, The Education University of Hong
Kong; Sohana Wadud Riwa Ahmad, The Education
University of Hong Kong; Jianjing Tang, The Education
University of Hong Kong; Yixing YANG, The Education
University of Hong Kong; Allan David Walker, The
Education University of Hong Kong*

Chair: *Michael Ota, Kennesaw State University*

Discussant: *Jeff Walls, University of Iowa*

**49.045. “Be Real Black For Me”: Black Livingness in
Children’s Literature - From Past to Present to Hopeful
Futures.** SIG-Literature; Symposium

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Santa Barbara C; 7:45-
9:15am

Participants:

Hairtales: A Multimodal Analysis of Self & Self-Expression of
Black Girls’ Hair in Children’s Literature. *Reka C. Barton,
University of Maryland*

Examining Narratives of Black Livingness Through a Critical
Content Analysis of Contemporary African American
Picturebooks. *Wintre Foxworth Johnson, University of
Virginia; Jennifer Danridge Turner, University of Maryland*
A Multimodal Critical Discourse Analysis of Unspeakable: The
Tulsa Race Massacre. *Vivica Joines, University of Maryland*
Flights, Talking Images, and Subverted Gazes: Returning to the
Heartbeat of Black Children’s Literature. *Latoya M. Teague,
University of Tulsa*

Chairs: *Latoya M. Teague, University of Tulsa; Reka C. Barton,
University of Maryland*

Discussants: *Wanda M. Brooks, Temple University; Desiree W.
Cueto, University of Arizona*

**49.046. Exploring Cultural Cost Among Students with
Minoritized Identities Across Varying Sociopolitical
Contexts.** SIG-Motivation in Education; Symposium

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Beaudry B; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Black Students’ Engineering Pathways: The ET Enigma.
*Revathy Kumar, University of Toledo; Joshua Archer,
University of Toledo*

Feeling “Less Relevant in the Context of Physics”: Exploring
Cultural Cost Among Minoritized Physics Students.

Danielle N. Berry, University of Oklahoma; Alison C. Koenka, University of Oklahoma; Kanvarbir Gill, University of Oklahoma; Korinthia D. Nicolai, Indiana University; Candace Andrews, University of Oklahoma; Maria Idrees, University of Oklahoma; Maisha Farzana Mumu, University of Oklahoma; Quynh P. Nguyen, University of Oklahoma; Benjamin C. Heddy, University of Oklahoma; Eric Abraham, University of Oklahoma

Not Just Fitting In: Belonging Opportunity Structures for Black, Latiné, and Indigenous Students in STEM. *Sanheeta Shankar, McGill University; Kristy A. Robinson, McGill University*

Unpacking Cultural Cost: "I don't see much culture, it's all really just math, math, math". *Korinthia D. Nicolai, Indiana University; Alison C. Koenka, University of Oklahoma; David Bryant Naff, Virginia Commonwealth University; Danielle N. Berry, University of Oklahoma; Amanda Vite, University of Southern California*

Chairs: *Danielle N. Berry, University of Oklahoma; Alison C. Koenka, University of Oklahoma*

Discussants: *Revathy Kumar, University of Toledo; Terah T. Venzant Chambers, Michigan State University*

49.047. Exploring the Sonic in Music Teaching & Learning.

SIG-Music Education; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Georgia I;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Exploring Soniclifeworlds Across Disciplines and Abilities: Histories, Theories, and Models of Practice. *jashen edwards, University of Guelph*

'Back' to Perceptual Basics: Embodied Metaphors in Music/Sound Pedagogy. *Rebecca Rinsema, Northern Arizona University*

Holding Sound: Interdisciplinary Pathways to Sound-Centered Teaching. *Gabriela Ocadiz, University of Arizona*

Sound, Sensation, and Difference: Troubling Sonic Governance in Music Education. *Noah Karvelis, Northern Arizona University*

Performatively Voicing the Political Educational Economies: What Studying Sound Can Do for and to Educational Researchers. *Walter S. Gershon, Rowan University; Boni Wozolek, Pennsylvania State University - Abington*

Chair: *Walter S. Gershon, Rowan University*

Discussant: *Walter S. Gershon, Rowan University*

49.048. Black Leadership, Faith, and Educational

Transformation. SIG-Research Focus on Black Education; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304B;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Employing the Legacy of the Black Church's Prophetic Activism for Modern DEI Educational Initiatives. *Brooke*

Starks, Michigan State University; Michael L. Lachney, Michigan State University

Leadership Approaches to Combat Anti-Black Racism in K-12 Urban and Suburban Public Schools: A Narrative Inquiry. *Audrey Angelia Littlejohn, University of Toronto*

Uncovering Black Education's Red Clay Potters: Examining the Community Impact of Jeanes Teachers, 1907-1968. *Brittney Kilgore, University of Georgia*

Chair: *Judith I. Brooks-Buck, J. Brooks-Buck Educational Consulting*

49.049. Navigating Community Relations in Mathematics Education Equity Research: Insights from Early Career Scholars. SIG-Research in Mathematics Education; Structured Poster Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 515B;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

1. Rooted Beginnings: Relational and Relationally-Accountable Math Education Research with Latine Families in Portland (Poster 1). *Susana Beltran-Grimm, Portland State University*

2. Toward Culturally Relevant Data Science: Exploring Sociopolitical Data in Guam and Saipan Math Classrooms (Poster 2). *Richard Carlos L. Velasco, University of Florida*

3. La Lucha Sigue: Fighting to Sustain our Commitments when the Community Hurts (Poster 3). *Sandra Zuniga, San José State University*

4. Towards Spatial Justice: Navigating Belonging and Boundaries in a Community-Centered Professional Learning Alliance (Poster 4). *Cathery Yeh, University of Texas at Austin*

5. Relational Noticing: Co-Constructing Math Meaning with Families at Home (Poster 5). *Daniela Alvarez-Vargas, University of Denver*

6. Co-constructing a Learning Community to Nourish, Empower, and Sustain Teachers in their Commitments to Justice (Poster 6). *Mallika Scott, California State University - Fullerton*

7. Reimaginando Professional Development: Centering Dual Language Mathematics Teachers' Cultural-Linguistic Repertoires (Poster 7). *Mariana Alvidrez, New Mexico State University*

8. Building Culturally Aligned Identities in a Middle School Math Classroom (Poster 8). *Salvador Huitzilopochtli, San Jose State University*

Chair: *Nickolaus A. Ortiz, Georgia State University*

Discussant: *Alfredo J. Artiles, Stanford University*

49.050. Programming, Professional Learning, and Instruction for Gifted Learners. SIG-Research on Giftedness, Creativity and Talent; Paper Session

Westin Bonaventure, Level 2, Echo Park; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Does Gifted Education Matter? A Quasi-Experimental Study of

Short- and Long-Term Outcomes. *Al Mansor Helal, University of Arkansas at Fayetteville; Rian R. Djita, University of Arkansas at Fayetteville; Jonathan Wai, University of Arkansas*

What Teachers Learned about Universal Screening with Local Norms: A Mixed Methods Evaluation Study. *Ann E. Robinson, University of Arkansas at Little Rock; Monica Meadows, University of Arkansas at Little Rock; Jill L. Adelson, Adelson Research & Consulting, LLC; Kishor Kumar, University of Arkansas at Little Rock*

Who's on the Committee Matters: Teachers' Beliefs about Inclusiveness in Gifted Education. *Todd Kettler, Baylor University; Yasmin Radinsky, Round Rock Independent School District; Nilay Gunel, Baylor University*

Two Hands Are Better Than One to Differentiate. *Del Siegle, University of Connecticut; D. Betsy Mccoach, University of Connecticut; Ashley Y. Carpenter, College of William & Mary; Susan Dulong Langley, University of Connecticut; Kelly L. Kearney, University of Connecticut; Kenneth J. Wright, Talcott Mountain Science Center and Academy; E. Jean Gubbins, University of Connecticut*

Differential Effects of an Advanced Mathematics Curriculum: A Cluster Analysis of High-Potential English Learners. *Gulnur Ozbek, St. John's University; Vinh Quang Tran, St. John's University; Seokhee Cho, St. John's University; Jenny Yang, St. John's University*

Chair: *Deborah D. Dailey, University of Central Arkansas*

Discussant: *Matthew C. Makel, University of Calgary*

49.051. Improving Rural Students' College Persistence: Using Cultural Assets and Innovative Programming for College Completion. SIG-Rural Education; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Georgia II; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Montana 10 Randomized Controlled Trial: Experimental Evidence for Comprehensive Rural Student Support. *Alyssa Ratledge, MDRC*

Train in Place: Place-Based Nursing Education Models in the Rural Mountain West. *Colleen Falkenstern, Western Interstate Commission on Higher Education*

Rural Black Students' HBCU Access and Navigation in Alabama's Black Belt. *Travis C. Smith, Alabama State University*

Chair: *Sabrina Klein, MDRC*

Discussant: *Marjorie L. Dorime-Williams, MDRC*

49.052. Bringing Science to Life through Innovative Science Intervention for Chemistry and Physics High School Students. SIG-Science Teaching and Learning; Symposium
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, San Fernando; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Cultural-Pedagogical-Content Knowledge: A Framework for

Equitable Science Teaching. *Clausell Mathis, Michigan State University*

Designing and Revising Instructional Resources and Professional Development Programs for Meaningful and Rigorous Science Education. *Ozlem Akcil Okan, Michigan State University; Joseph S. Krajcik, Michigan State University; Clausell Mathis, Michigan State University; Lucky Chukwudalu Nonyelum, Create for Stem Institute; Mathilda Smith, Michigan State University*

Contextually Informed Science Assessment: Exploring Student Responses at the Intersection of Science and Real-world Issues. *Angie Valbuena Rojas, Michigan State University; William Van Luven, Michigan State University; Daihui Xiao, Michigan State University; Lucky Chukwudalu Nonyelum, Create for Stem Institute; dee dubose, Michigan State University; Sheneka M. Williams, Michigan State University*

Navigating Partnerships: Factors Shaping Implementation of Research-Practice-Partnership to Improve Teaching and Learning of High-School Sciences. *Lena J. Walton, Alabama A&M University; Samantha L. Strachan, Alabama A&M University; Randy Barbour, Alabama A&M University; Barbara Schneider, Michigan State University*

Chair: *Lydia Bradford, Northwestern University*

Discussant: *Tony T. Latiker, Jackson State University*

49.053. Self-Study of Teacher Education Practices SIG Business Meeting. SIG-Self-Study of Teacher Education Practices; Business Meeting
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Atrium II; 7:45-9:15am

Chair: *Monica Taylor, Montclair State University*

Officers: *Katie F. Whitley, Montclair State University; Kelly Lormand, Grand Valley State University*

49.054. Inclusive Education Through Instructional Practices and Peer Relationships. SIG-Special and Inclusive Education Research; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum A; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Modeling What's Possible: Inclusive Demonstration Sites as Catalysts for Trust and Transformation in Education. *Meghan E. Cosier, Chapman University; Andrew F Wall, Fenix Research and Evaluation; Audri Sandoval Gomez, Chapman University; Kaylie Holke, Chapman University; Carmen Hopkins, Riverside County Office of Education*

Rethinking Inclusive Practices: Teachers' Practices and Students' Experiences in Chinese Mainstream Classrooms. *Ping Dong, University of Southampton; Kyriaki Messiou, University of Southampton; Charis Voutsina, University of Southampton*

"Words Don't Hold Together": An Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis of Reading Journeys on the Autism Spectrum. *David D. Yang, Western Washington*

University

Understanding Peer Relationships for Adolescent Girls with ADHD: Content Analysis on Voices Shared on TikTok. *Xinxia Li, The George Washington University; Elisabeth K. Rice, The George Washington University; Stacey Martino, The George Washington University*

How Peers Interact in Inclusive Schoolyards – Profiles of Peer Interactions and Their Correlates. *Katja Scharenberg, Ludwig Maximilian University of Munich; Hannah Decker, University of Education - Freiburg; Sebastian Röhl, University of Education - Freiburg; Wolfram Rollett, University of Oldenburg*

Chair: *Tamara Handy, Teachers College, Columbia University*

49.055. Spirituality and transcendence. SIG-Spirituality & Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum B; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Dialogic Education as a Source of Inclusive Spirituality. *Miguel Ángel Ángel Pulido-Rodríguez, Ramon Llull University; Anna Eva Jarabo, Ramon Llull University; Josep-Maria Canal-Barbany, Valencian International University; Paula Cañaveras-Martínez, University of Barcelona*

Perceptions of the Divine in Secular Spaces: A Study of U.S. Public-School Teachers. *Nicholas C. Block, Biola University; Dennis Eastman, Biola University*

Whispers Behind the Classroom Door: Exploring Ethical Tensions in Qualitative Research within Religious Girls' Education. *Zehavit Gross, Bar-Ilan University*

Spirituality Scholarship in Adult Education and Human Resource Development, 2000-2025: A Literature Review. *Jieun You, Valdosta State University; Shannon Perry, Valdosta State University*

Chair: *Aya M. Isaac, University at Albany - SUNY*

Discussant: *Marcia Theresa Caton, Molloy University*

49.056. Navigating Language, Identity, and Culture. SIG-Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis; Paper Session
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 6th Floor, Broadway; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

A Systematic Analysis of Return Migrant Students' Experiences in Mexican Higher Education: Challenges and Opportunities. *Elida Sanchez-Cruz, Universidad Veracruzana; Jenifer Crawford, University of Southern California*

Culture Matters for Teachers' Emotion Regulation and Its Relations to Their Well-being: A Three-Level Meta-analysis. *Hongbiao Yin, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Xijing Wang, The Chinese University of Hong Kong*

Development of Civic Identity among College Students: A Systematic Literature Review. *Jeff Ching-Fan Lai, University of Iowa*

How long do students take to exit English learner status? A meta-analysis of reclassification survival curves. *Taiyo Itoh, University of Oregon*

49.057. Computational Thinking and Cognitive Skill Development. SIG-Technology, Instruction, Cognition & Learning; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, San Gabriel A; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Exploring Factors Affecting Computational Thinking through Machine Learning and Multilevel Modeling Methods. *Tzu-Wei Wang, Virginia Commonwealth University; Michael Broda, Virginia Commonwealth University; Christine Lee Bae, Virginia Commonwealth University; Monty Jones, Virginia Commonwealth University*

Predictive Modeling Of Student Behavior In Virtual Reality: A Machine Learning Approach. *Prabeen Giri, Truman State University; Xinhao Xu, University of Missouri; Hao He, Emporia State University; Jhon Bueno-Vesga, Pennsylvania State University; Shangman Li, University of Missouri; Gayathri Sadanala, Truman State University*

The Relationship between Perceived Authenticity and Cognitive Engagement: Using Functional Near-Infrared Spectroscopy (fNIRS) Measurements. *Haotian Yang, University of Georgia; Ikseon Choi, Emory University; Richard Lamb, University of Georgia*

WMC Moderates Visual-Emotional Effects on Cognitive Load in Multimedia Learning. *Yijing Zhang, East China Normal University; Zhe Wang, East China Normal University*

Guiding Online Students' Cognitive Presence in Asynchronous Online Discussion: Application of GPT-4.0. *Larisa A. Olesova, University of Florida; Christine Wusylko, Kennesaw State University; Bojan Lazarevic, University of Florida; Swapna Kumar, University of Florida*

Chair: *Charles E. Flowers, California State University - Fullerton*
Discussant: *Hannah M Grossman, University of California - Los Angeles*

Division and SIG Roundtables

49.058. AERA Roundtable Session Friday 7:45 am; Roundtable Session

49.058-1. Internal and External Forces Shaping Principal Leadership (Table 1). Division A - Administration; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Scared Leadership: A Grounded Theory of Fear and Compliance in Public Education. *Meghan Beth Buchanan, Texas State University*

To Voice or not to Voice? Principals' Experiences with Exercising Voice in Schools and Districts. *Kimberly Jamison, University of North Carolina - Wilmington*
The Influence of External Pressures and School Leader Support on Civic Education Teachers. *Koon Lin Wong, The Education University of Hong Kong; Ming Ming Chiu, The Education University of Hong Kong; Kerry J. Kennedy, The Education University of Hong Kong; Ki Keith Chan, The Education University of Hong Kong; Soobin Choi, The Education University of Hong Kong*

Re-examining the Principalship in times of Change: Conceptualising Principal Agency. *Paul Campbell, The University of Hong Kong*

Chair: *Natasha N. Johnson, Augusta University*

49.058-2. Leadership Orientation Cross Diverse Contexts

(Table 2). Division A - Administration; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Hong Kong Principals' Identities in A Highly Dynamic Sociopolitical Landscape: A Narrative Study. *Miao Liu, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Haiyan Qian, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Yingying Huang, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Jiachen LIU, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Qin Zhang, Chinese University of Hong Kong*

Distributed Leadership Practices According to the Comprehensive Assessment of Leadership for Learning (CALL) in Taiwan and American Elementary Schools. *Yi-jung Wu, National Kaohsiung Normal University*

How Does Distributed Leadership Enhance Teacher Innovativeness? The Mediating Roles of Teacher Self-Efficacy and Collaboration. *Yang Yu, Shanghai Jiao Tong University*

Social Network Perspectives to School Leadership: Principals as Brokers. *Qin Zhang, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Haiyan Qian, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Miao Liu, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Jiachen LIU, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Yingying Huang, Chinese University of Hong Kong*

Collectivism Vs Individualism: The Relationship Between Principals' Zhongyong Thinking And Teachers' Career Adaptability. *Min Qi, Beijing Normal University; Yufeng Zhang, Beijing Normal University*

Chair: *Lina Safa, Pepperdine University*

49.058-3. Leading in a Rapidly Advancing Digital Landscape: Technology, Crisis, and the Future of Educational Leadership (Table 3).

Division A - Administration; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

AI Versus Human Approach to Educators' Problem of Practice: A Comparative Sensemaking Analysis. *Dominic Siami Egure, Oklahoma State University; Olajumoke Beulah Adigun, Oklahoma State University; Kolawole Michael Afolabi, Oklahoma State University; Oguns Clement Audu, Oklahoma State University; Oluwayemi Osite, ECHO Education Nigeria*

Evolving Education in the Age of Technology: Unforgetting histories, imagining futures. *Bryan Southworth, University of Connecticut*

Improving Efficacy: Using Mixed-Reality Simulation to Develop Self-Awareness in Emerging School Leaders. *Demian Barnett, University of California - Los Angeles*

Preparedness for Leading Online in a Polycrisis, a Call to Action Framework. *Carol A. Mullen, Virginia Tech*

Chair: *Angela Crevar, Mercer University*

49.058-4. Erased, Buried, and Precarious Accountings of U.S. Students' Racialized Experiences (Table 4).

Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Analyzing how calls to 'restore community' erase legacies and student of color experiences of racism. *Manali J. Sheth, University of Illinois at Chicago; Jason Salisbury, University of Illinois at Chicago*

Bordering Schools: Racialized Precarious-Status Youth, Policy Gatekeeping, and Abolitionist Educational Futures. *Arlo Kempf, University of Toronto - OISE; Dennique Lavia, Justice for Children and Youth; Xun Ril Li, University of Toronto - OISE*

Buried Histories: Systemic Motivations for Omitting and Distorting Racial Trauma in U.S. History Education. *Marcus Johnson, Virginia Tech*

Critical Fabulation as Educational Methodology: Refusing Black Schoolgirls' Erasure in Racialized/Ableist Educational Contexts. *JaiOnna Terry, The University of Alabama; Nirmala Erevelles, University of Alabama*

Empathy as a Foundation for Global Citizenship Education. *AnnaLise Hoopes, University of California - Los Angeles*

Understanding Student Experiences with Discrimination in a Restorative District: A Latent Class Analysis. *Amanda J. Davis Simpfenderfer, College of William & Mary; Peter N. Knox, University of Vermont*

Chair: *JaiOnna Terry, The University of Alabama*

49.058-5. Feminist Practices/Emotional Labor: Examining Intersectional Educator Identity (Table 5).

Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Educating Like the Spring Rain: Feminist Practices of Women

Teachers in Chinese Schools. *Xin Yi Zhang, East China Normal University*

Emotional Labor Among TESOL Teachers of Color: A Poststructural Approach to Racialized Teaching Experiences. *Alexander Parker, Johns Hopkins University; Heather Mehrtens, University of Maryland, College Park*

“Once a Teacher, Now Invisible”: Reimagining Professional Identity in U.S. Education Among International Student Spouses. *Parya Jangjou Tazehkand, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Proposing New Directions on the Research of Language Teacher Emotion Labor: A Systematic Review. *Xinyu Hui, Xi'an Jiaotong-Liverpool University; Qian Wang, Xi'an Jiaotong-Liverpool University; Haibo Gu, Soochow University; Jeong Jin Yu, Xi'an Jiaotong-Liverpool University*

Teaching While Haunted: Black Women Professors and Leaders Navigating Educational Justice in Precarious Times. *Donna-Marie Cole-Malott, East Stroudsburg University of Pennsylvania*

49.058-6. Exploring the Intersections of Artificial Intelligence and Educational Research (Table 6). Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

AI as Guest, Wisdom as Teacher: Rebuilding Power Relations in Educational Technology through the Culturally Sustaining AI Framework. *Muhammad Hilal Sudarbi, University of Groningen*

Designing a Responsible AI Literacy Framework for Education: Integrating Ethics, Equity, and Empowerment. *Shahin Hossain, University of Maryland - Baltimore County; Wei Huang, University of Alabama; Jujia Li, University of Alabama; Syntia Hadis, Teachers College, Columbia University; Leqi Li, Pennsylvania State University; Samaa Haniya, Pepperdine University; Shapla Khanam, HELP University; Idowu David Awoyemi, University of Alabama; Sima Ahmadi, Kent State University*

From Uncertainty to Understanding: A YPAR Study Co-Investigating AI Readiness Across a High School Campus. *Paola Rosenberg, Claremont Graduate University; Vasu Bagga, University of California - Berkeley; Dheeraj Koppu, University of California - Los Angeles*

Chair: *Yan Jiang, Stanford University*

49.058-7. Living Indigeneity: Centering Critical Reflections, Epistemologies, and Reclamation for Diasporic Indigenous Communities (Table 7). Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Contending with Diasporic Indigeneities. *David W. Barillas Chón, University of Northern Colorado*

Living Indigeneity: Incorporating Indigenous epistemologies in identity and learning research. *Saskias Casanova, University of California - Santa Cruz; Melissa Mesinas, Whittier College*

Teaching Across Tensions: Xicanx-Indigenous Solidarities and the Stakes of Reclamation. *Gabriela Kovats Sanchez, San Diego Mesa College; Velma Calvario Tlahuancapa, San Diego City College*

Chair: *Melissa Mesinas, Whittier College*

Discussant: *Luis Urrieta, University of Texas at Austin*

49.058-8. Innovations in Re-Defining Effective School Leadership Styles (Table 8). SIG-Leadership for School Improvement; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Is Edger Leadership Transforming Education? Insights From Evidence. *Cecilia Azorin, University of Murcia; Mireia Civis, Ramon Llull University*

Measuring Market Orientation in Demonstration High Schools in China. *Deyun Yang, Harbin Normal University; Lawrence George Drysdale, University of Melbourne; David M. Gurr, University of Melbourne*

Unspoken Power: Hidden Curricula and Distributed Leadership in a K-12 Public School District. *Vernon L Walton, Alameda Unified School District*

49.058-9. School Discipline and Safety (Table 9). SIG-School Community, Climate, and Culture; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

“I Feel Like I Fit In”: Middle School Students’ Perceptions Of Psychological Safety. *Mitali Temurnikar, Boston University; Tina M. Durand, Boston University; Pei Wang, Boston University*

Discretion in Implementation: A Street-Level Analysis of Restorative Practices in Philadelphia Schools. *Taylor Stenley, Research for Action; Alexis O’Herrick, Research for Action*

Stopping violence before it starts: An analysis of how potential school gun attacks are exposed. *Daniel Hamlin, University of Oklahoma*

49.058-10. Community-Centered and Relational Approaches in Environmental Science and Engineering Education (Table 10). SIG-Environmental Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Study 1: Supporting pre-service teachers' self-efficacy to facilitate youth-led civic engagement programs for the environment. *Megan Ennes, University of Florida; Emily Cayton, Campbell University; Elle Henson, University of Florida*

From Voice to Action: Developing Environmental Care through curriculum Co-Design process. *Aakriti Bisht, University of California - Irvine; Rossella Santagata, University of California - Irvine; Symone Gyles, University of California - Irvine; Hosun Kang, University of California - Irvine; Yuxi Huang, University of California - Irvine; Taryn M. Williams, University of California - Irvine; Jennifer J. Long, University of California - Irvine; Sara Ludovise, Orange County Department of Education; Erick Valdez, Orange County Department of Education*

Engaging local expertise in community science. *Christopher Jadallah, University of California - Los Angeles; Heidi Ballard, University of California - Davis*

Revitalizing Traditions Through Critical Community Science and Creative Placemaking. *Kelsie Fowler, University of Washington*

Cultural Values in Data Visualization: Insights from Young Professionals in Environmental STEM Careers. *Victoria Nguyen, University of California - Irvine; Guadalupe Rosas, University of California - Irvine*

Chair: *Asli Sezen-Barrie, University of California - Irvine*

49.059. AERA Roundtable Session Friday 7:45 am - Gold 1; Roundtable Session

49.059-1. Roundtable Session 3: Student Learning and Development in College and Beyond (Table 1). Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Asian Pacific Islander Student Leaders: The Model Minority Myth and Mental Health Challenges. *Eugene Fujimoto, California State University - Fullerton; Linh Huynh, California State University - Fullerton; Chrisna Ung, California State University - Fullerton*

Emerging Through Adversity: An Exploratory Qualitative Study on Undergraduate Students' Identity Safety on HBCU Campuses. *Sharonda Clay, Howard University; Kimberley Edelin Freeman, Howard University*

Exploring approaches to accessing campus resources: Insights from racially minoritized students. *Oscar Patrón, Indiana University; Jenifer L. Berry, Indiana University; Steven Feldman, Indiana University*

49.059-2. Student Debt: Information, Decision-Making and Outcomes (Table 2). Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;

7:45-9:15am

Participants:

From College to Homeownership: The Relationship Between Undergraduate Major, Salary, Student Loan Debt, and Homeownership. *Roy Y. Chan, Lee University; Amy Li, Florida International University*

Reframing Value in Higher Education: Insights from Individual-Level Tuition Data. *Gregory C. Wolniak, Northwestern University; Mark Salisbury, Pathways Planning & Insights*

Refunds, Rationality, and Inequity: A Behavioral Economics Analysis of Student Loan Borrowing. *Nicole Marie Johnson, Howard University*

Understanding College Graduates' Debt Burden: The Role of Institutional and State Factors. *Rong Chen, Seton Hall University; Jennifer A. Delaney, University of California - Berkeley; Thong Trinh, University of California - Berkeley*

49.059-3. Refusal, Care, and Justice: Educators Challenging Structures in Teaching (Table 3). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Enactment of Care, Labor & Devotion: Black Women Teaching for Liberation. *Makaela Jones, University of California - Berkeley*

Sacred Refusal in the Classroom: Black Women Educators, Leadership, and the Rest They're Deprived Of. *Lashante Mystic Briscoe, Northcentral University*

The Role of Whiteness in Teacher Beliefs and Practice. *Jaylene Patterson, University of Kentucky*

The Walls Are Closing In: Reinforcing Social Studies Teacher Restrictions, Surveillance, and Harmful Ideology on Departmental Group Dynamics. *Michael A. Kreckler, Baylor University; Kevin R. Magill, Baylor University; Liz Harrelson Magill, Baylor University*

"You're Representing a Movement Larger Than Yourself": Counter-Storytelling and Solidarity-Building in the Teaching of Palestine. *Rubén A. González, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Haia Z Haidari, The Ohio State University*

Chair: *Makaela Jones, University of California - Berkeley*

49.059-4. Teachers as Agents of Equity: Data, Democracy, and Instructional Change (Table 4). Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

"Equitable" Grading Through the Eyes of Teachers. *David Griffith, Thomas B. Fordham Institute*

Race/Ethnic Congruence and Algebra I Success Among Texas Middle School Students. *Jacob Kirksey, Texas Tech University; Raven Morris, Texas Tech University; Sarah*

Stultz, Texas Tech University

Reclaiming Public Education: Reviving Civic and Democratic Schooling in the Age of Neoliberal Standardization. *Johanna Barnhart, Hunter College - CUNY*

“What Does the Data Tell Us?”: Reimagining Data Use Research for Instructional Improvement. *Adejah Taylor, University of California - Los Angeles*

Discussant: *Walter M. Stroup, University of Massachusetts - Dartmouth*

49.059-5. Markets, Media, and the Politics of School Choice (Table 5). Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Competing for 4-year-olds: Public Discourse on the Impact of Pre-kindergarten on Private Child Care. *Lauren C. McKenzie, University of Texas at Austin*

Attitudes About a Counter-Cultural Educational Policy: A study of the new school choice system in Chile. *Cristian Cabalin, Universidad de Chile; Yahira Larrondo, Universidad Tecnológica Metropolitana*

Markets, Metrics, and Opportunity Gaps: Turkish Teachers' Perspectives on Neoliberal Restructuring. *Orbay BAŞARAN, Eskişehir Osmangazi University; Hamit Ozen, Eskişehir Osmangazi University*

Chair: *Tom Shields, University of Richmond*

49.059-6. Allies or Agendas? The Politics of Educational Partnerships (Table 6). Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Interrupted Progress: Navigating the Sudden Termination of a Grant Funded Research-Practice Partnership (RPP). *Patricia L. Reeves, Western Michigan University; John L. Lane, Michigan State University; Jianping Shen, Western Michigan University*

Military-Industrial Partnerships in Higher Education: A Comparative Study of MIT and Tsinghua University's Roles in National Security. *Yi Wu, Pennsylvania State University*

Partnering for Prekindergarten Focus Groups with Child Care Directors. *Sharon Ryan, Rutgers University; Karin Garver, Rutgers University*

Philanthropists and Funders as the Engine of the Science of Reading Reform Movement. *Elena Aydarova, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Chair: *Nora Reikosky, University of Houston*

Discussant: *La Toya Caton, Teachers College, Columbia University*

49.059-7. Non-academic Outcomes and Student Well-being:

The Importance of Schools and Communities (Table 7). Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

“Building the Plane as We Fly It”: Lessons from a Slashed Wraparound Program. *Cheyenne Phillips, Southern Methodist University; Shanae Neal, Southern Methodist University; Shanea Neal, Southern Methodist University; Alexandra E. Pavlakis, Southern Methodist University; Kessa Roberts, Clemson University; Meredith Paige Richards, Southern Methodist University*

Does Parental Academic Socialization Mitigate or Exacerbate Family Background Disadvantages? Predicting Problem Behaviors in Migrant and Local Adolescents. *Wei Wu, Peking University; Yanan Zhang, Renmin University of China*

Trauma Sensitive Schools and Communities: Early Findings from the PHASeS Evaluation. *Sarah A. Cordes, Temple University; Crystal Austin, Temple University; Maia B. Cucchiara, Temple University; Xu Jiang, Temple University; Thierry Elin-Saintine, Stockton University; Lori A. Shorr, Temple University; Julie Whalen McIntyre, School District of Philadelphia*

Chair: *Dion Burns, Learning Policy Institute*

49.059-8. Beyond Neutrality: Decolonizing English Language Teacher Education (Table 8). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Decolonizing TESOL Teacher Education: Neoliberal and Colonial Dynamics in Chinese EFL Teachers' Overseas Learning Journeys. *Fan Yang, Pennsylvania State University*

EFL Teachers' Emotional Labor on the Margins: Intercultural Teaching in Chinese Vocational Schools. *Di Wu, University of Cologne*

English Linguistic Neo-imperialism and English Language Teacher Education in Vietnam: An Autoethnographic Poetic Phenomenological Inquiry. *Ngoc Kim Tuyen Pham, Texas Tech University; Ngan Thi Thu Nguyen, Texas Tech University; Loan Thi Quynh Cao, Thompson School District*

Neutrality or Normativity? Pre-Service TESOL Teachers' Language Ideologies in a Global Englishes Context. *Onur Özkaynak, The Ohio State University*

The English Problem, Power and Paradox: Egyptian Teachers Navigating Neocolonial Policies in Cairo's International Schools. *Alia Shalaby, Pennsylvania State University*

Chair: *Alia Shalaby, Pennsylvania State University*

49.059-9. Children's Perspectives (Table 9). SIG-Early Education and Child Development; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

When Children's Meanings Meet Adult Frameworks: A Narrative Review of Literature on Epistemological Misalignments. *Tran Templeton, Teachers College, Columbia University; Sidney Hacker, Teachers College, Columbia University*

"I'm callin' a meeting!": Routines of Empowerment in Early Childhood Communities. *Dana Frantz Bentley, Buckingham Browne and Nichols School*

Remembering to Reimagine: Education for Sustainability with Toddlers in Swedish Preschools. *Deniz Pamuk, Mersin University*

"It's Important to Have Windows so You Can Get Sunlight": Understanding Children's Perceptions of Quality in Early Childhood Education and Care Settings. *Samantha Burns, University of Guelph; Jesseca Perlman, University of Toronto - OISE; Michal Perlman, University of Toronto - OISE*

Encouraging Children's Voices in Early Childhood Education and Care: Dialogic Interaction Based on Photo Elicitation. *Heli Johanna Muhonen, University of Jyväskylä; Mimmu Sulkanen, University of Jyväskylä; Maarit Alasuutari, University of Jyväskylä*

Chair: *Tran Templeton, Teachers College, Columbia University*

49.060. AERA Roundtable Session Friday 7:45 am - Gold 2;
Roundtable Session

49.060-1. Teacher and Caregiver Well-being and Professional Identity (Table 1). SIG-Early Education and Child Development; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

The Weight of Care: Vicarious Trauma and Self-Efficacy Among Head Start Educators. *Elizabeth Urgell, Florida International University; Rashmi Sharma, Western Illinois University; Hongwei Yang, University of West Florida*

Re-centering Relational Pedagogy: A Case Study of Affective Touch and Attachment in Infant Care. *Na Ra Yun, California State University, Dominguez Hills*

Early Childhood Leaders' Sleep Quality: Associations with Well-being and Working Conditions. *Timothy G. Ford, University of Oklahoma; Eleanor Su-Keene, Texas A&M University; Kyong-Ah Kwon, University of Oklahoma; Alison Wilson, University of Houston*

Examining Classroom Quality as a Moderator in the Association between Teacher Well-being and Teacher-Child Relationships. *Junghyun Min, University of Oklahoma; Kyong-Ah Kwon, University of Oklahoma; Timothy G. Ford, University of Oklahoma*

A Phenomenographic Study on Professional Agency of Kindergarten Teachers Working with Socio-Economically Disadvantaged Children. *Chrysa Pui Chi Keung, Education University of Hong Kong; Yinuo Wang, The Education University of Hong Kong*

Chair: *Timothy G. Ford, University of Oklahoma*

49.060-2. Motivation and Engagement in Second Language Learning: Growth Mindset, Self-Efficacy, and Resource Use (Table 2). SIG-Second Language Research; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Bouncing Back and Moving Ahead: A Meta-Analysis of Resilience and Motivation in Second Language Learning. *Xinjie Chen, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Zhenyi ZHOU, Chinese University of Hong Kong*

Living the Language: Student Engagement and L2 Learning Resource Use through Lens of Experiential Learning. *Xiaole Shan, Fordham University*

Motivation for Learning L2, Goal-Setting, and Self-Regulated Learning Among Arab Students with Learning Disabilities. *Randa Khair-Abbas, Arab Academic College for Education in Israel - Haifa; Vered Vaknin-Nusbaum, Western Galilee College; Zaki Kamal, Arab Academic College for Education in Israel - Haifa*

Shame and Growth Mindset in Second Language Learning: Mediating Roles of Motivation, Self-Efficacy, and Self-Regulation. *Pengpeng Cai, Trinity College Dublin; Xuhong Li, City University of Hong Kong; Xin Guan, Hong Kong Baptist University*

The Role of Native English-Speaking Volunteers in Ecuador's EFL Classrooms: A Qualitative Case Study. *Ligia Fernanda Espinosa-Cevallos, Kansas State University; Eder Intriago Palacios, Kansas State University; Antonieta Morales, Kansas State University; Maria Jose Hernandez, Universidad Regional Amazonica Ikiam*

49.060-3. Scaffolding Learning with AI (Table 3). SIG-Technology as an Agent of Change in Teaching and Learning; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Looking for help: A test to see if AI can help create social studies scaffolds that provide key assistance for ELLs. *Tierney B Hinman, Auburn University; Jesus Tirado, Auburn University; Jamie Harrison, Auburn University; Matthew F. Summerlin, Auburn University; Megan Andrews, Auburn University; Sarah I. Bailey, Opelika City Schools; Anna Poole, Auburn University*

Use of AI-based Scaffolding in Writing: Longitudinal Impact on Critical Thinking. *Qi Sun, University at Albany - SUNY;*

Alanda Joseph, University at Albany - SUNY; Cong Wu, University at Albany - SUNY; Gabriel Schlomer, University at Albany - SUNY; Tianlin Wang, University at Albany - SUNY

A Multi-Paradigmatic Perspective Towards the Adoption of Artificial Intelligence in Education. *Haidee A. Jackson, University of Texas - Permian Basin; Suman Rath, Montclair State University*

AI Scaffolding for Self-Regulated Learning in Graduate Research: A Mixed-Methods Study. *Jiahui Qi, East China Normal University; Jun Xu, East China Normal University; Yutian Gao, East China Normal University*

Chair: *Tuba Yilmaz, University of Utah*

49.060-4. Developing Faculty as Scholars (Table 4). SIG-

Faculty Teaching, Evaluation, and Development; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Achievement Goals and Creative Research Engagement: Investigating Motivational Processes in Germany and Türkiye. *Martin Daumiller, Ludwig Maximilian University of Munich; Merve Zayim-Kurtay, Middle East Technical University*

Beyond Retirement: Institutional Logics and Governance of Faculty Rehiring in China's Double First-class Universities. *Tianyu Wang, Xiamen University*

Perceived Institutional Support, Motivation, and Expectation Clarity: Indirect Pathways to STEM Faculty Research Success. *Percy Chris Kpodo, University of North Dakota; Godwin Ahiase, University of North Dakota; Robert H. Stupnisky, University of North Dakota*

Scholarship Re Re-Considered: Taking Stock of "Boyer-ness" in Contemporary U.S. Higher Education. *Laura Cruz, Pennsylvania State University; Scott Greenberger, Grand Canyon University*

The Role of Grit in STEM Faculty Research Success: A US Longitudinal Study. *Godwin Ahiase, University of North Dakota; Robert H. Stupnisky, University of North Dakota*

49.060-5. Global Indigenous Futures: Collaboration, Climate, and Knowledge in Motion Across the Americas (Table 5).

SIG-Indigenous Peoples of the Americas; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

A Collaborative Vision for a Proposed Special Issue on Indigenous Education Initiatives in Texas. *Marissa Munoz, University of Texas - San Antonio; Pablo Montes, Texas Christian University; Marleen Villanueva, Texas Christian University*

Socioenvironmental Crisis and Childhood in Mapuche Land:

Children's Maps and Narratives in Rural Education. *Maria Isabel Reyes, Pontificia Universidad Catolica de Valparaiso; Rukmini Becerra-Lubies, Pontificia Universidad Catolica de Chile*

Title: Participatory Needs Assessment: Biocultural Knowledge and Conservation Education in the Colombian Amazon. *Carolina Simon-Pardo, University of Florida; Jose Zafitama, Casa del conocimiento Education Institution K-12; Julie Brown, University of Florida; Yue Li, University of Florida*

Transformations in Social Technologies of Ribeirinhos Communities in the Brazilian Amazon in the Face of Climate Change. *Inny Accioly, Universidade Federal Fluminense; Arlete Gomes dos Santos, Universidade Federal Fluminense*

Chair: *Kavya Sree Mariboyina, Little Priest Tribal College*

49.060-6. International and Comparative Perspectives on Language Education (Table 6). SIG-Bilingual Education Research; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Change in Chinese Language Classroom Practices in Singapore: Evidence from the CORE Research Programme. *Hock Huan Goh, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University; Dennis Kwek, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University; Hwei Ming Wong, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University*

From Refugee Camps to College Classrooms: How the Past Informs the Present and Shapes the Future for Refugee Students. *Yacoub Aljaffery, Augsburg University*

Incremental Pathways to Educational Transformation: Transcultural Dialogue as a Tool to Develop Critical Cultural Competence. *Kristen L. Pratt, Western Oregon University; Ya-Fang Cheng, Western Oregon University; Bogum Yoon, Binghamton University - SUNY*

KnowledgeMatters for Educating Multilingual. *Claudia Peralta, Boise State University*

Spatializing language policy pluralities: A Comparative Case Study of two Estonian Upper Secondary Schools. *Kara D. Brown, University of South Carolina; Kadri Koreinik, University of Tartu*

49.060-7. Technology, AI, and Digital Identities in Language Learning (Table 7). SIG-Bilingual Education Research; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Exploring Structured GenAI Applications in Bilingual Multicultural Education: Opportunities from Student Experiences and Reflections. *Nesma Ragab Nasr, Northern Arizona University; Tonia F Bauer, University of South*

Carolina - Upstate; Chih-Hsiung Tu, Northern Arizona University; Laura Esthela Sujo-Montes, Northern Arizona University

Immersion e Identidad: Enfoques Translingüísticos En La Creación De Espacios Virtuales Educativos Multilingües. *Lourdes Cardozo-Gaibisso, Mississippi State University; Georgia Wood Hodges, University of Georgia*

The Development of Digital Identity Texts in Online Mandarin Classrooms: A Multiple Case Study. *Chuan Liu, Western University; Zheng Zhang, Western University; Rachel May Heydon, University of Western Ontario*

Utilizing translanguaging and AI to support intercultural competencies during learner exchange in Azerbaijan: A self-study. *Rashad Khalilov, Azerbaijan University of Languages; Emma R. Britton, University of Missouri - St. Louis*

49.060-8. Community-based bilingual experiences rooted in el suelo y sustento de la familia. (Table 8). SIG-Bilingual Education Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

“We should speak 100 percent Nepali.” Translanguaging Perspectives and Practices of a Bhutanese Refugee Family. *Tirtha Karki, Purdue University; Wayne E. Wright, Purdue University*

Building Inclusive Capacity in Chinese Immersion Early Childhood Settings. *Chu Hsi Tseng, San Francisco State University*

Child Agency in Family Language Policy: Reimagining Immigrant Parents' Perspectives and Educational Futures. *Izolda Savenkova, University of Maryland, College Park; Xinhang Hermione Hu, University of Maryland; Yige Zou, University of Washington*

Do We Align? Parents' and Teachers' Perceptions of Dual Language Learners' Social Competence in Preschool. *Jun Wang, The Ohio State University; Rachel Hur, Johns Hopkins University; Lieny Jeon, University of Virginia*

Engaging Families of Multilingual Learners: Co-Creating an Online Caregiver Course with Diverse Stakeholders. *Hazel Vega, Clemson University; Emily S. Howell, Clemson University; Lindsey W. Rowe, Clemson University; Katie Crook, Clemson University; C.C. Bates, Clemson University*

49.061. AERA Roundtable Session Friday 7:45 am - Gold 3; Roundtable Session

49.061-1. Illuminating Student Perspectives of Mathematics Classrooms (Table 1). SIG-Research in Mathematics Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Examining the Mathematical Conceptions Used by Multilingual Learners Speaking Spanish Versus English. *Melissa A. Gallagher, U.S. Math Recovery Council; Jessica H. Hunt, North Carolina State University; Temple A. Walkowiak, North Carolina State University; David W. Shaffer, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Brendan R. Eagan, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

“People Can See How Other People’s Minds Work”: Students’ Perspectives on Work-Sharing Across Two Classrooms. *Miriam Simone Leshin, University of Virginia*

Reconceptualizing Smartness: Student Perspectives in the Community College Mathematics Classroom. *Gabriela M. Hernandez, San Diego State University; Charles E. Wilkes, University of California - Davis; Mary E. Pilgrim, San Diego State University*

Student Self-Positioning and the Development of Mathematical Competencies. *Annie Zhou, University of Michigan*

Youth Perspectives on Societal Narratives about the Usefulness of Mathematics: Considering Individual and Relational Utility. *Tracy Dobie, University of Utah; Bailey N. Ondricek, University of Utah; Liza Romina Escobar, University of Utah*

Chair: *Daniel Ness, St. John's University*

49.061-2. Digital Technology in Career and Technical Education & Workplace Learning (Table 2). SIG-Career & Technical Education and Workplace Learning; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

CE Teach: Online Professional Development for CTE Faculty Coming into Teaching from Industry. *Svetlana Darche, WestEd; Joy Lewis, WestEd*

Reimagining TVET in the Digital Age: A Conceptual Framework for Internet of Everything Integration. *Zeinab Mokhtari, Dresden University of Technology; Ghasem Salimi, Shiraz University - Iran; Ali Akbar Safavi, Shiraz University - Iran; Thomas Koehler, Dresden University of Technology*

The Connotation, Conceptual Framework, and Development Pathways of Digital Competence for Vocational College Teachers. *Yihe Huang, Beijing Normal University*

Chair: *Anthony M. Perry, University of North Dakota*

Discussant: *Anthony M. Perry, University of North Dakota*

49.061-3. Youth and Advancing Family-School Partnerships (Table 3). SIG-Family, School, Community Partnerships; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Opportunity in Uncertain Times: Community-Based Organizations, Immigrant Youth, and Access to Capital

Amid Policy Threats. *Staci Pippin-Kottkamp, Bellarmine University*

Evaluating a Program Designed to Improve High School Progress Among Foster Care Youth: Educational Liaisons. *John H. Hitchcock, Westat; Jeffrey A. Anderson, Indiana University; Nell Krahnke, Indiana University; Eishi Adachi, Westat*

Parent and Caregiver Perceptions of a Community Youth Literacy Center: A Case Study. *Laveria Hutchison, University of Houston; Tairan Qiu, Stanford University; Elisa M. Holcomb, University of Houston; Jordyn Alyse Simmons, University of Houston; Brian Ellison, Project Row Houses; Xin Li, University of Houston; Sunny Stubbs, University of Houston*

Examining School Contexts for Centering Families and Youth within a Violence Risk Assessment. *Andy Garbacz, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Sinéad O'Neill, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Maria Fernanda S Cunha, University of California - Berkeley*

Chair: *Linxi Lu, University of Chicago*

49.061-4. Remixing Curriculum: Pedagogies, Technologies, and Literacies (Table 4). SIG-Hip Hop Theories, Praxis & Pedagogies; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

THE POETICS OF EXISTENCE: Poems as Critical Literacies of Hip-Hop Based Education. *Imani J. Wallace, University of Massachusetts - Amherst*

Hip Hop Aesthetics in Educational Research and Practice. *Roya Fathalizadeh, Arizona State University; Eric Alvarez, Arizona State University*

Hip-Hop Pedagogy as a Transformative Framework for Teacher Development. *Edmund S. Adjapong, Seton Hall University*

Lyrics of Learning: Chinese Hip-Hop as Informal Education Through Reality Pedagogy and Ratchetdemic. *Renda Sun, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Using Hip Hop Pedagogy and Digital Music Technology to Engage Students in STEAM Activities. *Cameron DeLeon Denson, North Carolina State University; Gregory Corbett, North Carolina State University*

Chair: *Qiana Cutts Givens, Mississippi State University*

49.061-5. Holistic and Community-Based Learning Approaches (Table 5). SIG-Holistic Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Alhambra Wellbeing Perspective: A Vision for Transforming Education Research. *Hessa Al-Thani, Qatar University*

From Anxiety to Agency: Reimagining Composition Pedagogy Through Black Feminist Praxis. *Elizabeth Labanna Harney,*

North Dakota State University

Grad CAFE: A New Community-Based Approach to Mentoring Centered Around Food. *Celeste Atkins, University of Arizona; Nicole Marrone, University of Arizona; Christina Kael, University of Arizona*

Education, Literacy and Decolonization in Cuba: An Exploration of Cuban Independence from the USA, Spain, and the Soviet Union. *Anna Grigoryeva, University of Maryland*

Holistic and Transformational Learning in Medical School: Seeking an Integrated Professional Identity. *Michelle L. Tichy, Alfred University*

Discussant: *Patience Amadu, University of Colorado - Colorado Springs*

49.061-6. Braiding Care and Cultural Wealth: Latinx Praxis, Mentorship, and Institutional Reckoning in Academia (Table 6). SIG-Latina/o/x Research Issues; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Femtorship, Mentorship, and Tormentorship: Unraveling a Trenza of Experiences Among Chicana/Latina/Afro-Latina Scholars. *Melissa A. Martinez, Texas State University; Mónica Byrne-Jiménez, UCEA; Soribel Genao, Queens College; Maritza Lozano, California State University - Fullerton; Sylvia Mendez-Morse, Texas Tech University; Rosa L. Rivera-McCutchen, Hunter College - CUNY; Mariela Aime Rodriguez, University of Texas - San Antonio; Estela Zarate, Loyola Marymount University*

"I just love helping people" - Ethic of Care by Latino Men in HESA Graduate Programs. *Hermen Diaz, Buffalo State University - SUNY; Lazaro Camacho, University of Rhode Island; Diana Cervantes, University of Texas at Austin*

Nuestra Testimonio/Our Testimony: Mentoring Through the Lens of Cultural Wealth. *Anita C. Hernandez, New Mexico State University; Monique Evette Matute-Chavarria, New Mexico State University; Minea Armijo Romero, New Mexico State University*

Personal and Professional Motivations of Latino Men in Higher Education and Student Affairs Master's Programs. *Lazaro Camacho, University of Rhode Island; Hermen Diaz, Buffalo State University - SUNY; Diana Cervantes, University of Texas at Austin*

Safety as a Basic Need: How Institutions Create Safety Insecurity for Latinx Graduate Students. *Ariana Lucia Garcia, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*

Chair: *Stephanie Luna-Lopez, University of California - Davis*

49.061-7. Cultivating Resistance and Belonging: Latinx Educational Pathways, Counterspaces, and Cultural Survival (Table 7). SIG-Latina/o/x Research Issues; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Creating Counterspaces: Empowering Latina Girls in STEM through Culturally Sustaining Pedagogy and Community Cultural Wealth. *Tadria Cardenas, University of California - Davis; Margarita Jimenez-Silva, University of California - Davis; Mayra Nuñez Martinez, University of California - Davis; Ashley Coughlin, Arizona State University*

Culturally Responsive Evaluation as Fugitive Pedagogy: Doing Right by our Latinx Students in Hostile Times. *Rick Sperling, St. Mary's University (TX); Teresita Munguia, Our Lady of the Lake University; Vanessa Clark, Our Lady of the Lake University*

Discrimination and Drive: How Mental Health Shapes Educational Values in Latinx Adolescents. *Manuel Teran Hernandez, University of Maryland; Richard Quentin Shin, University of Maryland; Carlos Santos, University of California - Los Angeles*

Emerging from the Third Space: Narratives of a Second-Generation Salvadoreña. *Jessica Flores, University of Colorado - Boulder*

Chair: *Jessica Flores, University of Colorado - Boulder*

49.061-8. Shaping Identities, Relationships, and Worlds Through Digital Literacies (Table 8). SIG-Writing and Literacies; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Memoir in the Machine: Teaching Memoirs and Biographies as Counter-Archives in the Digital English Classroom. *Abdul-Qadir D. Islam, Teachers College, Columbia University*

The Emotional Labor of Holding Digital Literacies. *Layla Coleman, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Unfolding Spatial Histories: A Postdigital Study of GeoGuessr Gameplay. *Liyan Yang, University of Kansas*

The Social Fabric of Reading: Hybrid Literacy Infrastructures, Reader Identity, and Collective Reading Practices. *Maggie Bryant, Baylor University*

Chair: *Abdul-Qadir D. Islam, Teachers College, Columbia University*

49.061-9. Stories on the Move: Tracing the Flows of Student's Embodied Literacies (Table 9). SIG-Writing and Literacies; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Tracing Embodied and Aesthetic Interpretations in Students' Readings of *Salvage the Bones*. *Beth Krone, Kennesaw State University*

"It got me going into a story": Multiperspectival Learning through Drama Integration. *Jacqueline Winsch, University of*

Pennsylvania; Lauren Borrasso, St. Laurentius School
Acting Virally: Postdigital Metatheatricality in Children's Playmaking. *Clara Abbott, University of Pennsylvania*
Embodied Literacies for Preschoolers with Diverse Abilities: Developing Inclusive, Drama-Based Storytimes in a Research-Practice Partnership. *Katie Bernstein, Arizona State University; Lauren van Huisstede, Arizona State University; Scott C. Marley, Arizona State University; Erin Rotheram-Fuller, Arizona State University; M. Adelaida Restrepo, University of South Florida; Theresa Moen, Arizona State University; Sepide Pazhouhi, Arizona State University; Jenny Millinger, Childsplay Theatre Company; Kathryn Brantley, Childsplay, Inc; Jennifer Gantwerker, Childsplay Theatre Company; Kim Manning, Childsplay Theatre Company; Alex Frost, Childsplay Theatre Company; Diane Salazar, Phoenix Elementary School District; Angela Edington, Phoenix Elementary School District*
Chair: *Jacqueline Winsch, University of Pennsylvania*

49.062. AERA Roundtable Session Friday 7:45 am - Gold 4;
Roundtable Session

49.062-1. RT4: Modeling Complex Data and Patterns:

Bayesian, Longitudinal, and Machine Learning Approaches (Table 1). Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Examining Moderation Effects in Latent Growth Model using A Bayesian Moderated Nonlinear Factor Analysis. *Suyoung Kim, University of Chicago; Jiwon Kim, Northwestern University; Brian T. Keller, University of Missouri*

Evaluating Bayesian Variable Selection Approaches for Nonlinear Random Effects Models. *Yue Zhao, University of Minnesota; Nidhi Kohli, University of Minnesota; Eric F. Lock, University of Minnesota*

Modeling Cyclic Patterns Using a Two-Stage Hybrid Bayesian Approach. *Han Du, University of California - Los Angeles; Brian T. Keller, University of Missouri; Lijuan Wang, University of Notre Dame*

A Cross-Classified Model Using Curricular Complexity to Predict Graduations. *Michael D. Toland, University of Toledo; David Dueber, University of Toledo; Gregory Heileman, University of Arizona; Steven Dandeneau, Colorado State University; Erin Helbig, Damour Systems; Hayden Free, Damour Systems*

Applying Machine Learning Approaches with Administrative Data to Investigate Student Level Outcomes: An Application with Kindergarten Entry Assessments. *Kristen E. Wright, University of North Carolina at Charlotte; Kyle T. Cox, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Richard G. Lambert, University of North Carolina - Charlotte*

49.062-2. Memory as Method: Black Epistemologies, Counterspaces, and Ancestral Inquiry in Qualitative Research (Table 2). Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Black History as a Palimpsest: Honoring the Past—Liberating Present Mindsets. *LaFrance A. Clarke, Independent Researcher*

Countering the Narrative: The Role of Research Methods in Examining Black STEM Possible Selves. *Brandi Cannon-Force, Stanford University*

Daddy Lessons: Metaphor, Memory, and the making of a Daughter Scholar. *Martha Clavelle, Grossmont College*

Chair: *Martha Clavelle, Grossmont College*

49.062-3. Supporting Student Transitions and Postsecondary Pathways (Table 3). Division H - Research, Evaluation and Assessment in Schools; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

The Impact of English Proficiency Designation on High School Students' English Language Arts and Reading Course-Taking Paths. *Micaela Maria Bonilla, Stanford University; Eunjung Myoung, Stanford University; Guillermo Solano-Flores, Stanford University*

Student and Educator Perceptions of the Value of Dual-Credit Courses. *Madison E. Andrews, University of Texas at Austin; Kait Ogden, University of Texas at Austin; Matthew S. Giani, University of Texas at Austin*

Student and Staff Perspectives on the Challenges and Opportunities of the Middle-to-High School Transition. *Yixuan Zhuang, Boston College; Christine Power, Medfield Public Schools; Cuiyun Liu, Boston College; Nat Vaughn, Medfield Public Schools; Nathaniel J. S. Brown, Boston College*

Work-Based Learning and Student Outcomes: Evidence from Pennsylvania's Secondary CTE Students. *Rosemary Riccardo, Lancaster Lebanon IU13; Brian Hutchison, Lancaster Lebanon IU13; Candy M. Miller, Lancaster Lebanon IU13*

Chair: *Mehmet Dali Ozturk, College of the Sequoias*

49.062-4. Reimagining Assessment for Equity and Student Learning Across Educational Contexts (Table 4). Division H - Research, Evaluation and Assessment in Schools; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Disparities in School Climate: Examining Equity Across Socioeconomic Status, Gender Identity, and Race/Ethnicity.

Aakash Arvind Chowkase, Yale University; Jessica D. Hoffmann, Yale University; Jennifer Seibyl, Yale University; Kalee DeFrance, University of British Columbia - Okanagan

Leveraging Teacher Expertise: A Research-Practice Partnership Approach to Equitable Kindergarten Readiness Assessment Reform. *Maia Elkana, Washington University in St. Louis; Jennifer Burris, University of Kentucky*

Reflective Assessment to Enhance Shared Epistemic Agency in Collaborative Inquiry and Knowledge Building. *Lei Ding, University at Albany - SUNY; Jianwei Zhang, University at Albany - SUNY; Thomas Underwood, University at Albany - SUNY; Dongni Guo, University at Albany - SUNY; Alae Sherafat, University at Albany - SUNY*

Reimagining Large-Scale Assessment Systems to Support Civic Learning. *Laura S. Hamilton, National Center for the Improvement of Educational Assessment, Inc.; W.*

Christopher Brandt, Center for Assessment

Chair: *Melissa L. Gholson, University of Kansas*

49.062-5. Growing Together: Social, Emotional, and Collaborative Learning (Table 5). Division I - Education in the Professions; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

An Examination of Social Learning Processes Associated with First Year Residents' Experiences with Surgical Training. *Rebekah Pollock, Georgia State University; Jonathan D. Pollock, Emory University; J. Luke Galloway, Emory University; Johanna M. Hinman, Emory University; Margaret Kennedy, Emory University; Jahnavi K. Srinivasan, Emory University*

An Exploration of Emotions, the More Competent Other, and Learning Among First Year Surgical Trainees. *Rebekah Pollock, Georgia State University; Jonathan D. Pollock, Emory University; J. Luke Galloway, Emory University; Johanna M. Hinman, Emory University; Margaret Kennedy, Emory University; Jahnavi K. Srinivasan, Emory University*

Efficacy of peer teaching in interprofessional group learning: A mixed-method exploration. *Helen Qing He, University of Hong Kong; Jiahao Liang, University of Hong Kong; Ying Ye, University of Hong Kong; Fraide A. Ganotice, University of Hong Kong*

How does teamwork satisfaction enhance student engagement in interprofessional education? A structural equation model. *Fraide A. Ganotice, University of Hong Kong; John Ian Wilzon Tolentino Dizon, University of Hong Kong; Helen Qing He, University of Hong Kong; Xiaoi Shen, University of Hong Kong; George L. Tipoe, University of Hong Kong*

Chair: *Dandan Chen, Mass General Hospital/Harvard Medical School*

49.062-6. AI as a Literacy Partner (Table 6). SIG-Instructional Technology; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

AI as a Literacy Partner: Enhancing Reading Comprehension and Creative Writing in Primary Education. *Panayiota H. Diakou, Cyprus' Ministry of Education; Charoula M. Angeli, University of Cyprus*

Cutting through Complexity: Utilizing GenAI Chatbot to Support Reading Comprehension. *Sotheara Veng, University of Delaware*

Enhancing Vocabulary Retention in EFL Learning: The Role of Generative AI Chatbots with Metacognitive Scaffolding. *Nanzhu Zhang, Beijing Normal University; Linyi Yong, Beijing Normal University; Yu Zhu, Beijing Normal University; Siqi Li, Beijing Normal University; Yi Zhang, Beijing Normal University; Peidi Gu, Beijing Normal University; Shuai Zhang, Anhui Normal University*

Using AI-assisted tools to enhance secondary students' writing performance and metacognition. *Wing Kiu Leung, The Chinese University of Hong Kong*

49.062-7. AI and Immersive Technologies: Exploring Emerging Tools for Assessment and Feedback (Table 7).

SIG-Classroom Assessment; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Designing Authentic Assessment with Virtual Reality and AI: A Systematic Review. *Emmanuel Chukwunonye Amaechi, University of Calgary; Kim H. Koh, University of Calgary; Xia Chao, Duquesne University; Mawuli Kofi Tay, University of Calgary*

Evaluating GenAI Feedback in Classroom Assessment: A Meta-Synthesis. *Elie Chingyen Yu, University at Albany - SUNY; Carla Evans, Center for Assessment*

An AI Framework for Identifying Uncertainty and Weaknesses in Written Responses to Usable Knowledge Tasks. *Namsoo Shin, Michigan State University; Xunlei Qian, Michigan State University; Yue Xing, Michigan State University; Cory S. Miller, Michigan State University; Joseph S. Krajcik, Michigan State University*

GenAI-Enhanced Automated Scoring of Scientific Explanation Open-Ended Responses Using Learning Progression Rubrics. *Lingxiao Hao, East China Normal University; Xiangdong Yang, East China Normal University; Guangzhen Gao, Jiangsu Normal University*

Chair: *Matthew Nyaaba, University of Georgia*

49.062-8. Mothering and Caregiving: Relational Praxis in Critical Qualitative Inquiry (Table 8). SIG-Qualitative Research; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Mexican Caregivers and Their Experiences with Educational Technology. *Elizabeth Serna, Portland State University; Sasha Reinwald Albrecht, Portland State University; Susana Beltran-Grimm, Portland State University*

By Sound and Image: Reimagining Plática as Method and Praxis for Mother-Scholars of Color. *Xiaoyi Wei, SUNY Brockport; Jacqueline Cofield, Hunter College - CUNY*

Motherscholarship Abroad: A Methodological Journey with a Ukrainian Refugee Community in Romania. *Elizabeth Bellows, Appalachian State University*

Chair: *Emily Dobrich, University of Toronto - OISE*

Discussant: *Astri Napitupulu, University of Missouri - St. Louis*

49.062-9. Diverse Applications of the Rasch Model (Table 9). SIG-Rasch Measurement; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Development and Validation of Vicarious Racism Survey for Graduate Students: Rasch Analysis. *Olukemi Olubunmi Kolawole, University of Kentucky; Jungmin Lee, University of Kentucky*

Psychometric Evaluation of the Career Values Survey Among Middle School Students: Evidence from Nonparametric and Rasch Analyses. *Justice Dadzie, University of Alabama; Daniel O. Oyeniran, University of Alabama; Joni M. Lakin, University of Alabama*

Chair: *Youn Seon Lim, University of Cincinnati*

49.062-10. Teaching and mentoring mixed methods research: Highlighting challenges and opportunities for novices and experts (Table 10). SIG-Mixed Methods Research

Cosponsored with SIG-Teaching and Learning Research Methods; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Demystifying Integration: Doctoral Strategies for Bridging QUAL + QUAN in Mixed Methods Research. *Monica Hernandez-Johnson, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Sheetal Survase, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Sarah Hahn Campbell, University of Northern Colorado; Ambrosia Daphne Solis, University of California - Riverside; Shannon Locke, University of Missouri; April Ursula Fox, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Nicole J. Thomas, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Nichole Fehrenbach, Johns Hopkins University*

Beyond Parallel Analysis: Iterative Proposition Testing for Mixed Methods Integration. *Bradley E. Cox, Michigan State University; Karly Ball Isaacson, Michigan State University; Brett Ranon Nachman, University of Pittsburgh; Yilun Jiang, Michigan State University; Rebecca Brower, Michigan State University*

The work of mixed methods dissertations: perspectives from

doctoral advisors through a mixed methods survey. *Jonelle Prideaux, University of Cincinnati; Vicki L. Plano Clark, University of Cincinnati*

Chair: *Paris D. Wicker, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

Division and SIG Posters

49.063. AERA Poster Session Friday 7:45 am; Poster Session

49.063-1. Unpacking the Intersections of Parent, Family and Community Engagement. Division A - Administration; Poster Session Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 7:45-9:15am

Posters:

1. Sanctuaries of Justice: The Black Church as a Site of Educational Advocacy, Memory, and Resistance (Poster 1). *Brandon La'Shaun Wooley, The University of Texas System; SeongGyeong Park, University of Texas at Austin*
2. The digital sphere and parental involvement: Mapping of the literature in the field (Poster 2). *Audrey Addi-Raccah, Tel Aviv University; Paola Dusi, Università degli studi di Verona*

49.063-2. Examining the Varying Effects of Juvenile Arrest on College Enrollment for Racially/Ethnically Diverse Youth: The Role of School-Level Factors. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Poster Session Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 7:45-9:15am

Poster:

3. Examining the Varying Effects of Juvenile Arrest on College Enrollment for Racially/Ethnically Diverse Youth: The Role of School-Level Factors (Poster 3). *Royel M. Johnson, University of Southern California; Hyung-Jung Kim, SUNY - Cortland*

49.063-3. Poster 1. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Poster Session Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 7:45-9:15am

Poster:

4. How Social Relationships Shape the Career Aspirations of Master's Students — A Longitudinal Study of Chinese Master's Students (Poster 4). *xinrui li, Zhejiang University*

49.063-4. Teacher Pipelines, Recruitment, and Pathways. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Poster Session Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 7:45-9:15am

Posters:

5. Exploring the SUM: Developing a Model of the Urban Mathematics Teacher Pipeline (Poster 5). *Celia Rousseau Anderson, University of Memphis*
6. From High School Teacher Academy to University Teacher Preparation: Understanding Student Pathways Through a Belonging-Centered Partnership (Poster 6). *Eric Hougan, Central Washington University*
7. How do diverse candidates enter the California teacher pipeline, whom do they teach, and do they stay? (Poster 7). *Thomas M. Smith, University of California - Davis; Tine F. Sloan, University of California - Santa Barbara; Yiwang Li, University of California - Riverside*
8. How Pre-Service STEM Teachers Use Their Networks to Learn about the Teaching Profession (Poster 8). *Janet Solis Rodriguez, University of Texas - San Antonio; Carrie Anna Mitchell, University of Texas - San Antonio; Priya Prasad, University of Texas - San Antonio; Carey B. Walls, University of Texas - San Antonio*
9. Student-Centered Approaches to Recruitment and Retention of Diverse STEM Teachers: CRT + Posthuman Interventions (Poster 9). *Jerry L. Rosiek, University of Oregon; Tristan G. Gleason, California State Polytechnic University - Humboldt; Sage Hatch, University of Oregon; Bradley Sullivan, University of Oregon; Presence O'Neal, University of Oregon*
10. The Beginning of the Teacher Pipeline: Which College Students Apply to Teacher Education Programs? (Poster 10). *Dan Goldhaber, American Institutes for Research; Roddy Theobald, American Institutes for Research; Amy M. Roth McDuffie, Washington State University; David Slavit, Washington State University - Vancouver; Jennifer Dechaine, Central Washington University; John Krieg, Western Washington University; Vivien W. Chen, The State of Washington; Emma Dewil, American Institutes for Research*
11. Toward "New Suns": Exploring the Intersections of Synchronous-Service and Grow Your Own Teacher Preparation (Poster 11). *Devon Hedrick-Shaw, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Acelynn C. Perkins, University of Colorado - Boulder*
12. Understanding Rural Teacher Retention in Chinese Rural Regions: A Social Capital Perspective on Border-Crossing Experiences (Poster 12). *Shuang XIE, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Si Chen, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Xi Lan, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Yun Dai, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Ming Dong Mak, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Mai Lu, China Development Research Foundation; Zhixin Du, China Development Research Foundation; Yiluo Mose, China Development Research Foundation*
13. Unforgetting Teacher Shortage Histories: Reimagining Leadership for Equitable Retention in California (Poster 13). *Pinyi Wang, University of Florida; Tiffany Shanice Aaron, University of Florida*
14. When Staying Becomes a Life Project: Unraveling

Reflexive Agency and Rural Teacher Retention in Urbanizing China (Poster 14). *Yuchen WU, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Jocelyn Wong, The Chinese University of Hong Kong*

49.063-5. AI Literacies in Teacher Education: Frameworks, Practices, and Ethical Engagement. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 7:45-9:15am

Posters:

15. Constructive Controversy with AI: Elementary Students Engage in Ethical Reasoning and Debate (Poster 15). *Tomas Galguera, Northeastern University; Lyndsay Schaeffer, Northeastern University*
16. Establishing a Global Community of Engaged Virtual Teaching: An Innovative Approach to Virtual Clinical Preparation (Poster 16). *M. Allison Witt, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*
17. Pre-Service Teachers' Experiences and Perspectives on Using Generative AI in Developing Teaching Materials (Poster 17). *Hyeonho Henry Yu, Ball State University; Moon-Heum Cho, Syracuse University; Seongmi Lim, Ball State University; EunHae Grace Park, Ball State University; So-Yeon "Sally" Kang, Ball State University*
18. Punctuating AI in the Classroom: A Design Case for Empowering Students with AI Literacy (Poster 18). *Nicole King, University of Rhode Island; Jialin Yan, University of Rochester*
19. Supporting Computer Science Teacher Education Pathway Development Through a Community of Practice: Insights from Stakeholders (Poster 19). *Yin-Chan Janet Liao, Georgia State University; Ijeoma Mbaezue, Georgia State University; Erin Anderson, Georgia State University; Jennifer Rosato, University of Minnesota; Michelle Friend, University of Nebraska - Omaha*
20. The CLEAR Framework: Enhancing Pre-service Teachers' AI Literacy via GAI Digital Storytelling (Poster 20). *chuangqi chen, Shanghai International Studies University*

49.063-6. K-12 Teacher Title Evaluation: Policy Implementation and Influencing Factors. Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 7:45-9:15am

Poster:

21. K-12 Teacher Title Evaluation: Policy Implementation and Influencing Factors (Poster 21). *Yifan Sun, Beijing Normal University*

49.063-7. ATL Poster Session 2: AI Integration and Outcomes in Postsecondary Settings. SIG-Advanced Technologies for Learning; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall -

Exhibit Hall A; 7:45-9:15am

Posters:

22. Classifying Permissiveness in Generative AI Syllabus Policies: A Corpus-Based Typology Development (Poster 22). *Amanda Taylor, Boise State University; Brett E. Shelton, Boise State University*
23. Explainability in Predictive Learning Dashboards: A Systematic Review of Educational Utility and Design Strategies (Poster 23). *Xianghui Meng, Columbia University; Shiyang Zhang, University of Pennsylvania*
24. Generative AI and Self-Directed Learning: A Systematic Review of Emerging Trends and Implications (Poster 24). *Xiaoying Zheng, Indiana University; Zixi Li, Indiana University; Chaoran Wang, Colby College*
25. Integrating Generative AI in Qualitative Analysis: Application in Science Education (Poster 25). *Rida Munir, Utah State University; Ha Nguyen, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Hillary Lucille Swanson, Utah State University; Ravi Sinha, Utah State University; Idris Solola, Utah State University*
26. Learning through Generative Questioning with Generative AI: An ICAP approach (Poster 26). *Lu Ding, University of South Alabama; Rachel Rodenberg, University of South Alabama; Erkan Er, Middle East Technical University; Ha Nguyen, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*
27. This Student Does Not Exist: A Scoping Review of Synthetic Data for AI in Education (Poster 27). *Sarah Burriss, Vanderbilt University; Golnaz Arastoopour Irgens, Vanderbilt University; Dan Carpenter, North Carolina State University; Ole Molvig*
28. Using Large Language Model to Analyze Chemistry Undergraduate Students' Self-Constructed Concept Maps (Poster 28). *Gan Jin, Washington State University; Tingting Li, Washington State University; Hyeonji Julia Lee, Washington State University; Yu Xue, Washington State University; Peng He, Washington State University; Oluwale Olalekan Adesope, Washington State University; Chloe G. Dydasco, Washington State University; Oluwafemi J. Sunday, Washington State University; Krista Nishida, Washington State University*
29. Developing and Validating a Scale for Artificial Intelligence Literacy (SAIL): A Mixed Approach (Poster 29). *Michael Yi-Chao Jiang, Shenzhen Technology University; Sanki Zu-Quan Shao, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Morris Siu-Yung Jong, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Ching Sing Chai, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Chin-Chung Tsai, National Taiwan Normal University*

49.063-8. Innovating Curricular Designs for Bilingual Teacher Education in the US: Programs, Policies and Partnerships. SIG-Critical Issues in Curriculum and Cultural Studies; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall -

Exhibit Hall A; 7:45-9:15am

Posters:

30. Advocating for LGBTQ+ Students in Bilingual Classrooms: Creating Solidarity and Building Coalitions Across Communities (Poster 30). *Carol Brochin, University of Arizona; Anthony Diaz-Vazquez, University of Arizona; Em Bowen, University of Arizona*
 31. Intertwined Gentrification Processes of U.S. Neighborhoods and Bilingual Education: Uncovering Possibilities of Resistance and Transformation (Poster 31). *James A. Gambrell, University of Northern Colorado; Garrett Delavan, University of New Mexico*
 32. The Need for Trauma-Informed Approaches in Bilingual Teacher Preparation (Poster 32). *Vanessa Santiago Schwarz, University of Colorado - Boulder; Ofelia Castro Schepers, Purdue University*
 33. Navigating Complexity: The Roles of Bilingual Teacher Educators as Policy Agents in University Teacher Preparation Programs (Poster 33). *Magaly Lavadenz, Loyola Marymount University; Jongyeon Joy Ee, Loyola Marymount University; Elvira G. Armas, Loyola Marymount University*
 34. Empowering Bilingualism: The Role of Culturally Responsive Leadership in Sustaining Culturally Sustaining Pedagogy (Poster 34). *Lourdes Vioria, Texas A&M International University*
 35. Integrating Technology into Bilingual Teacher Education Programs: Lessons from a Teacher Educator Affinity Group (Poster 35). *Jenia Marquez, City University of New York; Sarane James, City University of New York; Sara Vogel, City University of New York; Dominika McPartland, Hunter College - CUNY; Zena Cooper, Hunter College*
 36. From English-only to Renacimiento: The Role of State Policy Making and Grassroots Program Development in (Re)Building California's Bilingual Teacher Pipeline (Poster 36). *Adam Sawyer, California State University - Bakersfield; Adeli Ynostroza Ochoa, California State University - Bakersfield*
 37. Adding Critical Earth Consciousness to the Conversation on Critical Consciousness in Dual Language Bilingual Education: Two Case Studies (Poster 37). *Juan A. Freire, Brigham Young University; Garrett Delavan, University of New Mexico; Trish Morita-Mullaney, Purdue University; Erica Freire, None*
 38. Preparing Critically Conscious Bilingual Educators with a Global Perspective: Historical Foundations and Future Directions (Poster 38). *Cristina Alfaro, San Diego State University*
 39. Critical and Culturally Efficacious Bilingual Pedagogues: The Nautilus Shell as a Metaphor for Transformation and Transcendence in Biliteracy Practices (Poster 39). *Claudia T Garcia, University of Texas San Antonio; Belinda Bustos Flores, University of Texas - San Antonio; Juanita Santos, University of Texas - San Antonio; Claudia Cabrera, University of Texas - San Antonio*
 40. Understanding and Addressing Language Ideologies in Bilingual Teacher Education Programs (Poster 40). *Gilberto P. Lara, University of Texas - San Antonio; Kathryn I. Henderson, University of Texas - San Antonio; Kristen Lindahl, University of Texas - San Antonio*
- 49.063-9. Teaching in Exile: Embodied Pedagogies of Displaced Academics for Peace and Justice.** SIG-Critical Peace Education; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 7:45-9:15am
- Poster:
41. Peace Education Research: A Preliminary Bibliometric Analysis (2015-2025) (Poster 41). *Burhanettin Keskin, University of Mississippi*
- 49.063-10. Learning Sciences Poster Session.** SIG-Learning Sciences; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 7:45-9:15am
- Posters:
42. "Life emerging from the ashes": Systems thinking and emotional configurations in wildfire art and sense-making (Poster 42). *Molly L. Kelton, Washington State University; Elizabeth Grace, Washington State University; Patricia L. Saraniero, Moxie Research; Kristin Saba Fisher, Washington State University; Alex Lombardi, Eugene Science Center; Dave Jordan, Eugene Science Center*
 43. "That Would Be Confusing for Fifth Graders": Boundary Infrastructure Moves in a Research-Practice Partnerships (Poster 43). *Jody E. Clarke-Midura, Utah State University; Alireza Zandi, Utah State University; Sariah López-Fierro, Utah State University; Mimi M. Recker, Utah State University*
 44. "What's Next?": Mentorship Through A Storytelling Card Game (Poster 44). *Sonia Kim, Teachers College, Columbia University; J K Voorhis, Teachers College, Columbia University*
 45. A Review of Precollege Quantum Information Science Education through a Learning Sciences Lens (Poster 45). *Raquel Coelho, University of Pittsburgh; Kristin Borte, University of Bergen; Cassandra Kelley, University of Pittsburgh; Junyu Liu, University of Pittsburgh*
 46. Defining "Engagement": How Teachers Describe Student Engagement During a Digital Inquiry Module (Poster 46). *McKenna Lane, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Catherine L. Dornfeld Tissenbaum, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*
 47. Does feedback always increase learning from partial concept maps? (Poster 47). *Yuxin Ren, Huazhong University of Science and Technology; Zhe Wang, East China Normal University*
 48. Effects of Different Concept Mapping Activities on Learning Performance (Poster 48). *Qingyuan Liu, East*

China Normal University; Zhe Wang, East China Normal University

49. Into the Zone: Evaluating AI-Augmented Personalized Learning Through a ZPD-Aligned Metric (Poster 49). *Amanda Siebert-Evenstone, Age of Learning; Hee Jin Bang, Age of Learning*
50. Surveying Computing Identity in Childhood: A Practice-Linked Framework for Upper-Elementary Learners (Poster 50). *Nicholas LaGrassa, Northwestern University; Nayada Tantichirasakul, Northwestern University; Michael S. Horn, Northwestern University*
51. Teacher Conceptualization of Student Challenges and Solutions for CT in A Non-CS Classroom (Poster 51). *Vivek Sabanwar, Texas A&M University; Tugce Aldemir, Texas A&M University; Selcuk Kilinc, Texas A&M University; Ali Bicer, Texas A&M University; Donggil Song, Texas A&M University*
52. Unpacking Teacher Knowledge Creation in KNILT: Mixed-Methods Analysis of 36 Online Minicourse Designs (Poster 52). *Ying Kong, University at Albany - SUNY*
53. Using Conjecture Mapping to Evaluate Instructional Prompts for Collaborative Learning in a Game-Based Learning Environment (Poster 53). *Hyeongjo Kim, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Jina Kang, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*
54. Belonging at the Boundaries: Becoming an Elementary Computer Science Teacher through Curricular Co-Design (Poster 54). *Gregory Benedis-Grab, University of Colorado - Boulder; Alexandra Gendreau Chakarov, Colorado School of Mines*

49.063-11. Bridging Gaps in Education: Cultural Competence, Neuroscience, and Teacher-Student Interaction. SIG-Brain, Neurosciences and Education; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 7:45-9:15am

Posters:

55. Algebra Teaching That Breaks Racial and Gender Barriers: Cultural Competence, Self-Efficacy, and Culturally Relevant Neuroeducation (Poster 55). *Ranjini Mahinda JohnBull, East Carolina University; Yasemin Gunpinar, University of Texas - Tyler; Stephen J. Pape, Johns Hopkins University*
56. Exploring Neuroscience Education Programs for Primary Caregivers: A Systematic Literature Review (Poster 56). *Astrid Schmied, Nanyang Technological University - National Institute of Education*
57. The Correlation between Teacher-Student Interactive Learning and Students' Neurofunctional Development: A Systematic Review (Poster 57). *Jingwen Li, The Chinese University of Hong Kong, Shenzhen; Runke Huang, Chinese University of Hong Kong - Shenzhen*

49.064. e-Lightning Ed-Talk Session 10 - Stage 1. AERA e-Lightning Ed-Talks; AERA Ed Talk

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Exhibit Hall A - Stage 1; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

- Exploring the SUM: Developing a Model of the Urban Mathematics Teacher Pipeline (Stage 1, 7:50 AM). *Celia Rousseau Anderson, University of Memphis*
- Understanding Rural Teacher Retention in Chinese Rural Regions: A Social Capital Perspective on Border-Crossing Experiences (Stage 1, 7:59 AM). *Shuang XIE, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Si Chen, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Xi Lan, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Yun Dai, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Ming Dong Mak, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Mai Lu, China Development Research Foundation; Zhixin Du, China Development Research Foundation; Yiluo Mose, China Development Research Foundation*
- Constructive Controversy with AI: Elementary Students Engage in Ethical Reasoning and Debate (Stage 1, 8:08 AM). *Tomas Galguera, Northeastern University; Lyndsay Schaeffer, Northeastern University*
- Establishing a Global Community of Engaged Virtual Teaching: An Innovative Approach to Virtual Clinical Preparation (Stage 1, 8:17 AM). *M. Allison Witt, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*
- Punctuating AI in the Classroom: A Design Case for Empowering Students with AI Literacy (Stage 1, 8:26 AM). *Nicole King, University of Rhode Island; Jialin Yan, University of Rochester*

K-12 Teacher Title Evaluation: Policy Implementation and Influencing Factors (Stage 1, 8:35 AM). *Yifan Sun, Beijing Normal University*

Exploring Neuroscience Education Programs for Primary Caregivers: A Systematic Literature Review (Stage 1, 8:44 AM). *Astrid Schmied, Nanyang Technological University - National Institute of Education*

Algebra Teaching That Breaks Racial and Gender Barriers: Cultural Competence, Self-Efficacy, and Culturally Relevant Neuroeducation (Stage 1, 8:53 AM). *Ranjini Mahinda JohnBull, East Carolina University; Yasemin Gunpinar, University of Texas - Tyler; Stephen J. Pape, Johns Hopkins University*

Chair: *Terri D. Pigott, Georgia State University*

49.065. e-Lightning Ed-Talk Session 10 - Stage 2. AERA e-Lightning Ed-Talks; AERA Ed Talk
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Exhibit Hall A - Stage 2; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Using Large Language Model to Analyze Chemistry Undergraduate Students' Self-Constructed Concept Maps (Stage 2, 7:50 AM). *Gan Jin, Washington State University; Tingting Li, Washington State University; Hyeonji Julia Lee, Washington State University; Yu Xue, Washington State University; Peng He, Washington State University; Olusola*

Olalekan Adesope, Washington State University; Chloe G. Dydasco, Washington State University; Oluwafemi J. Sunday, Washington State University; Krista Nishida, Washington State University

Integrating Generative AI in Qualitative Analysis: Application in Science Education (Stage 2, 7:59 AM). *Rida Munir, Utah State University; Ha Nguyen, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Hillary Lucille Swanson, Utah State University; Ravi Sinha, Utah State University; Idris Solola, Utah State University*

Generative AI and Self-Directed Learning: A Systematic Review of Emerging Trends and Implications (Stage 2, 8:08 AM). *Xiaoying Zheng, Indiana University; Zixi Li, Indiana University; Chaoran Wang, Colby College*

Classifying Permissiveness in Generative AI Syllabus Policies: A Corpus-Based Typology Development (Stage 2, 8:17 AM). *Amanda Taylor, Boise State University; Brett E. Shelton, Boise State University*

Teacher Conceptualization of Student Challenges and Solutions for CT in A Non-CS Classroom (Stage 2, 8:26 AM). *Vivek Sabanwar, Texas A&M University; Tugce Aldemir, Texas A&M University; Selcuk Kilinc, Texas A&M University; Ali Bicer, Texas A&M University; Donggil Song, Texas A&M University*

A Review of Precollege Quantum Information Science Education through a Learning Sciences Lens (Stage 2, 8:35 AM). *Raquel Coelho, University of Pittsburgh; Kristin Borte, University of Bergen; Cassandra Kelley, University of Pittsburgh; Junyu Liu, University of Pittsburgh*

“What’s Next?”: Mentorship Through A Storytelling Card Game (Stage 2, 8:44 AM). *Sonia Kim, Teachers College, Columbia University; J K Voorhis, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Chair: *Yuane Jia, Rutgers University*

Friday, April 10th, 8:00 am

50.010. Routledge Editorial Meetings (Day 1). Affiliated Groups; Board Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Level 2, Silver Lake; 8:00am to 5:00pm

50.011. University of San Diego, School of Leadership and Education Sciences (SOLES) Breakfast. Affiliated Groups; Reception
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 5; 8:00-10:00am

Friday, April 10th, 9:00 am

AERA Related Activities

51.010. AERA Research Engagement and Development With Youth (READY) Program Session 3 (Invitation Only).

AERA Related Activities; Invited Speaker Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Room 306AB; 9:00am to 4:00pm

Chair: *Lori Diane Hill, American Educational Research Association*

Friday, April 10th, 9:45 am

Governance Meetings and Events

52.001. AERA Government Relations Committee: Closed Meeting.

AERA Governance; Governance Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 513; 9:45-11:15am

Chair: *Elizabeth H. DeBray, University of Georgia*

52.002. Educational Researcher: Closed Editorial Board Meeting.

AERA Governance; Governance Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 518; 9:45-11:15am

Chair: *John Neikirk, American Educational Research Association*

AERA Related Activities

52.010. Black Deans Coalition: Leading Through Complexity, Advancing Equity in a Time of Retrenchment (Closed Meeting).

AERA Related Activities; Invited Speaker Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 4; 9:45-11:15am

Chairs: *Tabbye M. Chavous, American Educational Research Association; Marvin Lynn, University of Colorado - Denver*

Presidential Sessions

52.011. From Memory to Movement: SECRET Work to Advance Science Literacy.

AERA Presidential Session; Invited Speaker Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 408A; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Science for Us: Engaging in Elementary Participatory Science for Community Change. *Terrance Burgess, Michigan State University*

Noticing and Futuring for Equity: Transformative

Commitments in Justice-Oriented Science Education. *Alexis Patterson Williams, University of California - Davis*

Changing of the (Van)Guard: Leaving Behind Apolitical Science Education. *Daniel Morales-Doyle, University of Illinois at Chicago*

Remaining Steadfast in the Pursuit of Justice-Oriented Science Education. *Tia C. Madkins, The University of Texas at Austin*

Maintaining Unapologetic Commitments to Racial Justice and Black Joy When Saying (and Being) Black is No Longer Popular. *Terrell R Morton, University of Illinois at Chicago*

Chairs: *Brian Williams, Brian Williams Science; John Settlege, University of Connecticut*

Discussant: *Bryan A. Brown, Stanford University*

52.012. Futuring Against the Grain: Doctoral Students Charting New Paths in Education Research. AERA Presidential Session; Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C; 9:45-11:15am

Chairs: *Cleveland Hayes, Indiana University - Indianapolis; Honey Walrond, University of California - Berkeley*

Participants: *Maria Cioe-Pena, University of Pennsylvania; Claudia G. Cervantes-Soon, Arizona State University; Ja'Nya Banks, University of California - Berkeley; Amura Cameron, Old Dominion University; Luis Alberto Legaspi, University of San Diego; Darion A. Wallace, Stanford University; Lucy Zhang, Teachers College, Columbia University*

52.013. The State of the K-12 Teaching Profession: Perennial Challenges and New Possibilities. AERA Presidential Session; Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 406AB; 9:45-11:15am

Chair: *Pamela L. Grossman, University of Pennsylvania*

Presenters: *Pamela L. Grossman, University of Pennsylvania; Maya Kaul, University of Pennsylvania; Sarah Schneider Kavanagh, University of Pennsylvania; Chandra L. Alston, Learning Policy Institute; Travis J. Bristol, University of California - Berkeley; Julie Jackson Cohen, University of Virginia; Kathlene Holmes Campbell, National Center for Teacher Residencies; Conra D. Gist, University of Houston; Roddy Theobald, American Institutes for Research*

Discussant: *Kent McGuire, William and Flora Hewlett Foundation*

AERA Research and Science Policy Sessions

52.014. Looking Forward: Research Recommendations for Early Childhood Curriculum. AERA Science and Policy Sessions; Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 408B; 9:45-11:15am

Chair: *Vivian L. Gadsden, University of Pennsylvania*

Participants: *Andres Sebastian Bustamante, University of California - Irvine; Caroline Ebanks, Teachers College, Columbia University; Wintre Foxworth Johnson, University of Virginia; Christine M. McWayne, Tufts University*

52.015. National Science Foundation: Supporting STEM Education Research and Innovation Funding Opportunities and Program Officer Roundtable. AERA Science and Policy Sessions; Invited Roundtable

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 404AB; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Dr. Sylvia Butterfield, Directorate Head, NSF Directorate for STEM Education. *Sylvia Margaret Butterfield, National Science Foundation*

Dr. Monya Ruffin, Deputy Directorate Head, STEM Education Research and Innovation, NSF Directorate for STEM Education. *Monya Aisha Ruffin-Nash, National Science Foundation*

Dr. Margret Hjalmarson, Section Head, STEM Education Research and Innovation, NSF Directorate for STEM Education. *Margret A. Hjalmarson, National Science Foundation*

Dr. Andrea Nixon, Section Head, STEM Education Research and Innovation, NSF Directorate for STEM Education. *Andrea Nixon, National Science Foundation*

Dr. Rabiah Mayas, Program Officer, STEM Education Research and Innovation, NSF Directorate for STEM Education. *Rabiah Marie Mayas, RMM Consulting*

Dr. Suazette Mooring, Program Officer, STEM Education Research and Innovation, NSF Directorate for STEM Education. *Suazette Mooring, Georgia State University*

Dr. Adrienne Stephenson, Program Officer, STEM Workforce and Talent Development, NSF Directorate for STEM Education. *Adrienne P. Stephenson, Florida State University*

Chair: *Monya Aisha Ruffin-Nash, National Science Foundation*

AERA Sessions

52.016. The Revision of the Testing Standards: Foundations (Invited Joint AERA/NCME Session). AERA Sessions

Cosponsored with NCME; Invited Speaker Session
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Wilshire Grand Ballroom III; 9:45-11:15am

Chair: *Ye Tong, National Board of Medical Examiners*

Participants: *Mark R. Wilson, University of California - Berkeley; Qiwei He, Georgetown University; Rochelle S. Michel, Smarter Balanced Assessment Consortium; Cara Cahalan Laitusis, Center for Assessment; Maria Marquine, University of California San Diego; Stephen E. Stark, University of*

South Florida; Michael C. Rodriguez, University of Minnesota

Discussant: Andy Reyes, University of Massachusetts - Boston

Committee Sessions

52.017. Division G Fireside Chat: Zine Making with The Queer Migrants of Color Archive. Graduate Student Council Cosponsored with Division G - Social Context of Education; Invited Speaker Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 402A;
9:45-11:15am

Chair: Kristina Johnson-Yates, Indiana University - Indianapolis
Speakers: Oluwaseun Oyindamola Ogunleye, University of Michigan; day parker, University of Michigan

52.018. Imagining the Future of Black and Brown Youth in (Carceral) Los Angeles. Committee on Scholars of Color in Education; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304A;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Carceral Cartographies: Black Foster Youth and the Paradox of Schooling in Los Angeles. Brianna Marche' Harvey, California State University - Fullerton

Things They Imagine: (Re) Imagination as a Tool for an Abolitionist Future. Pharren Miller, University of California - Los Angeles

Good Looking Out: Racially Minoritized Youth, Incarceration, and Care. Anibal Serrano, University of California - Irvine
Imagining, Creating, and Sustaining Alternatives for Racially Minoritized Youth: A Panel Discussion. Damien Sojoyner, University of California - Irvine; Anibal Serrano, University of California - Irvine; Pharren Miller, University of California - Los Angeles; Brianna Marche' Harvey, California State University - Fullerton

Chair: Uriel Serrano, University of Southern California

Discussant: Uriel Serrano, University of Southern California

52.019. Leadership and Faculty Development in International Education. International Relations Committee; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 502A;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Empathy, Empowerment, and Evolution: Rethinking Leadership Success in Lebanese Higher Education. Lina Safa, Pepperdine University

Faculty Development in Music under China's "Double First-Class" Higher Education Reform. Wanying Liang, University of Wisconsin - Milwaukee

Imagining the emancipatory future of the Expert Teacher designation: an international history of a phenomenon? Andy

C. Goodwyn, University of Reading

International Networking and Diverging Interests in Doctoral Education Research Communities Organized through Scientific Communication. Sverker Lindblad, Gothenburg University; Barbara Gross, Free University of Bozen-Bolzano

Chair: Fabian Barch, University at Buffalo - SUNY

Discussant: Kendall Dwayne Deas, University of South Carolina

52.020. Mentoring and Belonging in Research: Developing Centers that Champion Undergraduate Students as Social Justice Researchers. Social Justice Action Committee; Invited Speaker Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 511C;
9:45-11:15am

Chair: Gretchen Robinson, North Carolina A&T State University
Presenters: Stephen D. Hancock, North Carolina A&T State University; Nina L. Gilbert, Morehouse College; Fred A. Bonner, Prairie View A&M University

International Organization Sessions

52.021. Navigating Resistance in the Classroom: New Perspectives on a Familiar Challenge. International Aligned Organizations/Flemish Forum for Educational Research - VFO; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum B; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

IKNOW what you know – Development and validation of an instrument to gain insight into students' knowledge of instruction. Morane Stevens, KU Leuven; Fien Depaepe, University of Leuven; Katie Goeman, KU Leuven; Jan Elen, KU Leuven

Generative AI as Instructional Agents: International Students' Engagement and Resistance in Self-Regulated Learning. Juan Cai, Vrije Universiteit Brussel; Nadia Hugo, Vrije Universiteit Brussel; Artemis Pantou, Vrije Universiteit Brussel; Eleni Kougentaki, Vrije Universiteit Brussel; Koen Lombaerts, Vrije Universiteit Brussel

Chair: Morane Stevens, KU Leuven

Discussant: Veronica X. Yan, University of Texas at Austin

WERA Sessions

52.022. Re-Envisioning Infrastructure for the Advancement of Education Research Worldwide (WERA Session). World Education Research Association; Invited Speaker Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum C; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

The Leadership Role of Research Centers in International

Education Research and Innovation. *Eva L. Baker, University of California - Los Angeles*

Perspectives and Opportunities from the Vantage of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD). *Stephan Vincent-Lancrin, Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development*

The Role of the Equitable Education Fund as a Case in Point in Thailand. *Kraiayos Patrawart, Equitable Education Fund*

International Education Data as an Infrastructural Backbone for Knowledge Advancement. *Peggy G. Carr, National Center for Education Statistics, IES*

Open Access Publishing in Futuring Knowledge Diffusion, Use, and Impact. *Gustavo E. Fischman, Arizona State University*

Chair: *Felice J. Levine, AERA Emerita*

Division Sessions

52.023. Culturally Responsive Leadership for Social Justice.

Division A - Administration; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, La Brea; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Navigating Precarity: A Framework for System-Level Equity Leaders As Tempered Radicals. *Meghan Comstock, University of Maryland; Dayna Muniz, University of Pennsylvania*

School Leaders' Perspectives on Student Voice as a Culturally Responsive Practice. *Gina Marie Davenport, Notre Dame of Maryland University; Stephanie L Savick, Notre Dame of Maryland University; Angela L. Snyder, Notre Dame of Maryland University; Maisha Gillins, Anne Arundel County Public Schools*

Culturally Responsive Caring Principals: A Call for Anti-Carceral Leadership. *Ocheze Joseph, American University; Antonio L. Ellis, American University; William N. Thomas, American University; Shawn Joseph, Howard University; Rachelle S. Savitz, East Carolina University*

Culturally Responsive School Administrator Practices and Teacher Self-Efficacy in High-Needs Urban K-12 Schools. *Melody Mindell Hawkins, National University*

Equity Practice and Principal's Social Positioning: A Critical Social Network Case Study. *David Albert Rodes Trautman, University of California - San Diego*

Chair: *Marlinda Boxley, Bowie State University*

Discussant: *Karina Guerrero, Claremont Graduate University*

52.024. Equity by Design: Redesigning Principal Pathways for Systemic Change.

Division A - Administration; Symposium
Westin Bonaventure, Level 2, Beverly; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Seeing System Change: Social Network Analysis as a Formative Tool for Equity-Centered Implementation. *Yi-Hwa Liou, National Taipei University of Education;*

Daniella Molle, University of Wisconsin - Madison

Promising Practices Under Pressure: How ECPI Districts Keep Equity Work Alive. *John B. Diamond, Brown University; Daniella Molle, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Sensing the variation in the way district leaders perceive equity-centered schools. *Louis M. Gomez, University of California - Los Angeles; Mary Louise Leger, University of California - Los Angeles*

The CALL-OTL Survey as a Formative Feedback Support for School-Level Equity-Centered Leadership. *Richard R. Halverson, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

The MEI Study – Building System-Level Capacity for Equity Monitoring. *Alex J. Bowers, Teachers College, Columbia University; Christopher Saldaña, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Chair: *Will J. Jordan, The Wallace Foundation*

Discussant: *Shaun R. Harper, University of Southern California*

52.025. The fight continues: navigating restrictions on equity, social justice, and academic freedom.

Division A - Administration; Invited Speaker Session
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Los Feliz; 9:45-11:15am

Chair: *Liliana E. Castrellon, San José State University*

Participants: *Anindya Kundu, Florida International University; Maritza Lozano, California State University - Fullerton; Amanda U. Potterton, University of Kentucky; Samantha B. Cohen, American University; Melissa A. Martinez, Texas State University*

52.026. Pedagogies of Ignorance and Authoritarian Epistemologies: Cyborg Surveillance States, Meme Warfare, and MAGA Drag Queens.

Division B - Curriculum Studies; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 403B;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

@catturd2 and the Cyborgian Memeification of Ignorance. *Jake Burdick, Purdue University*

Name It and Reclaim It: Black Youth Using Social Media to Disrupt Pedagogies of Ignorance. *Janelle Grant-Ashbaugh, Grand Valley State University*

The Surveillance Cyborg: Palantir and the Posthuman Security Apparatus. *Jennifer April Sandlin, Arizona State University*

Lady MAGA: A Reactionary Queer Cyborg. *Erik L. Malewski, Kennesaw State University*

Enduring Logics of Fungibility: A Decolonial Reading. *Nathalia E Jaramillo, Kennesaw State University*

Deploying Ignorance as Resistance: Theorizing and Applying Posthuman Ignorance. *Alexander B. Pratt, University of Memphis*

Chair: *Erik L. Malewski, Kennesaw State University*

Discussant: *Denise M. Taliaferro Baszile, Wayne State University*

52.027. Division C Jan Hawkins Award (Arturo Cortez) and

Outstanding Early Career Scholar Award (Patrick Beymer) Invited Session. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Invited Speaker Session
Westin Bonaventure, Level 3, Avalon; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Jan Hawkins Winner: How to Create Justice-Oriented Technology for Teaching and Learning. *Arturo Cortez, University of California - Davis*

Early Career Award Winner Talk, Moments that Matter: What Intensive Longitudinal Methods Reveal about Student Motivation. *Patrick N. Beymer, University of Cincinnati*

Chair: *Helenrose Fives, Montclair State University*

Participants: *Daryl A. Tate, University of Arkansas at Little Rock; Cynthia Carter Ching, University of California - Davis; Benjamin C. Heddy, University of Oklahoma; Ji Y. Hong, University of Arizona; Kris D. Gutiérrez, University of California - Berkeley; Meca R. Williams-Johnson, Georgia Southern University*

52.028. How Data Science Education Can Enable Exploration of Real World Phenomena. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Structured Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 515A; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

1. Developing Critical Data Literate Girls in Informal STEM Settings (Poster 1). *Marc Sager, Southern Methodist University; Saki L. Milton, Southern Methodist University*
2. Climate Education & Field-Based Investigations (Poster 2). *Venicia Ferrell, Old Dominion University; Alexis Tharpe, Old Dominion University*
3. Supporting Justice-Oriented Data Literacy in Science and History Classrooms (Poster 3). *Bodong Chen, University of Pennsylvania; Regina Lisinker, University of Minnesota; Vivian Leung, Toronto Metropolitan University; David DeLiema, University of Minnesota; Cassandra Scharber, University of Minnesota*
4. Puffins!: Scientific Sensemaking to Improve Middle School Students' Attitudes Towards Data (Poster 4). *Jacob Sagrans, Tumblehome, Inc.; Janice R. Mokros; Pendred E. Noyce, Noyce Foundation*
5. Exploring Real-World Phenomena through Interest-driven Data Investigations in a High School Data Science Curriculum (Poster 5). *Rotem Israel-Fishelson, University of Maryland; David Weintrop, University of Maryland*
6. Embodying Data Points a Within Real-world Phenomenon (Poster 6). *Mengxi Zhou, Indiana University; Joshua Adam Danish, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*
7. Learning Data Through Embodiment of Real World Sports Movement (Poster 7). *Ashley Serine Quitaro, Northwestern University; Marcelo A.B. Worsley, Northwestern University*
8. Data Science Through Physical Computing in a Smart Greenhouse Project: A Case Study (Poster 8). *Jaai Uday Phatak, Boston College; Sheikh Ahmad Shah, Boston*

College; Avneet Hira, Boston College; Helen Zhang, Boston College; Michael Barnett, Boston College

9. Making Meaning with Data: Integrating Data Literacy in ELA (Poster 9). *Chris Cruz-Gonzalez, Indiana University; Merijke Coenraad, Digital Promise Global; Selena Steinberg, Indiana University; Mengxi Zhou, Indiana University; Joshua Adam Danish, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Chairs: *Marc Sager, Southern Methodist University; Katherine M. Miller, Concord Consortium*

Discussant: *Okhee Lee, New York University*

52.029. Advances in Psychometric and Machine Learning Approaches to Assessment. Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Paper Session
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 7th Floor, Hollywood Ballroom I; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Evaluation of Q-Matrix Validation Methods Under Attribute Hierarchies. *Tianpeng ZHENG, Peking University; Zehan Jiang, Peking University*

Research on Online Learning Experience Evaluation Based on LSTM Algorithm and Multimodal Data. *yiwei gou, East China Normal University; Yaofeng Xue, East China Normal University; Zhan Chen, East China Normal University; jialin zhou, East China Normal University; 扣琪 王, East China Normal University*

The Best of Two Worlds: An IRT-Enhanced Framework for Interpretable and Generalizable Automated Essay Scoring. *Wei Xia, East China Normal University; Haoran Shi, East China Normal University; Jin Wu, East China Normal University; Chanjin Zheng, East China Normal University*

Tracking Learning Trajectories in Fraction Addition and Subtraction Using Longitudinal Cognitive Diagnosis Modeling Framework. *Alvin Daiz Tenorio, University of the Philippines; Kevin Carl Pena Santos, University of the Philippines; Jose Quito Pedrajita, University of the Philippines*

When Cut Scores Impact Human Ratings: A Many-Facet Rasch Modeling Approach. *Kuan-Yu Jin, Hong Kong Examinations and Assessment Authority; Thomas Eckes, University of Bochum*

52.030. Innovations for Complexity in Models and Design: Inference, Estimation, Classification, and Longitudinal Issues. Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Paper Session
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 6th Floor, Metropolitan; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Centering Categorical Covariates in Cross-Classified Random Effects Models. *Young Ri Lee, Ewha Womans University*

How Small Is Too Small? Investigating Small Class Sizes in Growth Mixture Modeling Through Simulation. *Courtney*

Howard-Kirby, University of South Florida; Eunsook Kim, University of South Florida; Emma Elisa Evudóttir, University of South Florida - Tampa; Xilong Jing, University of South Florida; Yan Wang, University of Massachusetts Lowell; Xin Tong, University of Virginia; David Goretzko, Utrecht University; John M. Ferron, University of South Florida

Daily Diary Research in Education: A Primer for Researchers, Practitioners, and Policymakers. *Christina Scanlon, University of Chicago; Gregory Pollard, University of Chicago; Katherine Shah, University of Chicago; Ming-Te Wang, University of Chicago*

Estimation of Two-Level Hurdle Model with Two-Side Truncated Generalized Poisson Distribution using RTMB. *Jiachen Liu, Michigan State University; William H. Schmidt, Michigan State University; Barbara Schneider, Michigan State University; Richard T. Houang, Michigan State University; Yuehua Cui, Michigan State University; Haolei Weng, Michigan State University; David Yeager, University of Texas at Austin*

Post-Hoc Bayesian Hypothesis Testing for Improving Inference in Underpowered Educational Research Designs. *M. Shane Tutwiler, University of Rhode Island; Szu-Yu Zoe Kao, University of Rhode Island*

Chair: *Kelly Edwards, American Board of Pediatrics*

Discussant: *Bixi Zhang, Graduate Center - CUNY*

52.031. Reckoning with the Impact of Policy to Understand the Present. Division F - Historical Inquiry in Education; Paper Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 504; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

The Price of Cost Containment: A Critical Policy Analysis of the California Master Plan. *David O'Brien, California State University - Sacramento; Amal Kumar, California State University - Sacramento*

A Brief History of US School Bathrooms and How They Have Shaped Gender. *Jackie M. Blount, The Ohio State University*

The Fall of the Majority: The Politics of Educational Gatekeeping in Victorian England for Working-Class Britons. *Faith D. Northern, New York University*

Education at High Speed: Governance, Power, and Policy in North Dakota's Progressive Era. *Kevin Read, University of North Dakota*

The Outsourced High School: Revisiting Conant's Vision in a Moment of Polarity. *Dustin Hornbeck, University of Memphis*

Chair: *Sherman Dorn, Arizona State University*

Discussant: *Matthew G. Kelly, University of Washington*

52.032. Unforgetting Heroes at Los Angeles National Cemetery: Meeting 21st-Century Learning Goals through K12 Curriculum Development. Division G -

Social Context of Education Cosponsored with Spotlight on Los Angeles and the Region; Off-Site Visit
Los Angeles National Cemetery. 950 S Sepulveda Blvd, Los Angeles, CA 90049, Division G Tour; 9:45am to 1:45pm

Participants: *Deanna Cooke, Loyola Marymount University; Darin Earley, 5M Legacy Educational Consulting Services; Cynthia Ruiz, Loyola Marymount University*

52.033. Division H VP Session: Unforgetting Our United Division H History: A Journey through the Lens of Past Vice Presidents about Research, Evaluation, and Assessment in Our Schools and Hopes for the Future.

Division H - Research, Evaluation and Assessment in Schools; Workshop
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Wilshire Grand Ballroom I; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Division H: Inclusion of Graduate Students. *Vickie L. Cartwright, Broward County Public Schools*

Division H Inclusion of Novice Professionals. *Bradley J. McMillen, Wake County Public School System*

Division H Leadership Role Regarding Technology Use. *Joseph M. O'Reilly, Arizona State University*

Division H History, Development and Implementation of its Four Core Tenets into the Development of its By-laws. *Mary E. Yakimowski, Samford University*

Chair: *Virginia W. Snodgrass Rangel, University of Houston*

Participants: *Rachel E. Durham, Notre Dame of Maryland University; Chad T. Green, Loudoun County Public Schools*
Discussant: *Jennifer Leigh Whitson, Alexandria City Public Schools*

52.034. Accountability to What: Institution Responses to Shifting Equity Landscapes. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum G; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Affirmative Action After Students for Fair Admissions: Lessons for Sustaining Equity from the Global South. *Tafadzwa Tivarange, Spencer Foundation*

Analyzing the Impact of Performance-Based Funding on Enrollment, Selectivity, Outcomes, and Finance in Historically Black Colleges and Universities. *William Casey Boland, Baruch College - CUNY*

Out of the Shadows: General Counsels and Their Policymaking Role In College Admissions. *Kelly Slay, Vanderbilt University; Daniel Hay, Vanderbilt University*

Under Pressure: How Institutional and Political Influences Predict the Dismantling of DEI in Higher Education. *Dreama Heaven Rhodes, University of Michigan*

Early and Strategic: A Multi-Faceted, Low-Burden Approach to Advising First-Year College Students. *Francheska Olivia Jimenez, Teachers College, Columbia University; Yingxin*

Ye, Teachers College, Columbia University; Caron M. Mineo, Teachers College, Columbia University; Christine Banks Calderon, City College of New York; Meike Faber, City College of New York; Herbert Signoret, City College of New York; Ellen B. Meier, Teachers College, Columbia University

Discussant: *Eric R. Felix, San Diego State University*

52.035. Oppression and Agency: Marginalized Students

Navigating Higher Education. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum F; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

An Asset-Based Study on STEM College Student Mentors of Color's Perception of Leadership. *Ting-Han Chang, William Paterson University*

Examining Labor Among Black Collegiate Men in a Barbershop Talks Series. *Jarrod E. Druery, University of Cincinnati; Jason Ottley, SXSU*

Spillin' Tea: A Discourse Analysis of Black Collegiate Women's Experiences with Microaggression at a PWI. *Ekaete Udoh, University of Missouri*

The Effects of Men Peer Behavior on Women's Learning in Engineering Classrooms. *Selyna Perez Beverly, Eastern Michigan University*

Discussant: *Jessica C. Harris, University of California - Los Angeles*

52.036. Race and Diversity in Higher Education after Trump

2.0: Perspective from Four Books. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Symposium

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum H; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Before They Banned Critical Race Theory, They Banned Mexican American Studies: Lessons from Tucson. *Nolan L. Cabrera, University of Arizona*

"What If Your Research Is the Problem?" Repressive Legalism and Scholarly Resistance. *Richard J. Reddick, University of Texas at Austin*

Admissions after SFFA v. Harvard and Trump 2.0. *Julie J. Park, University of Maryland*

Reflections on Asian Americans and Affirmative Action Following SFFA v. Harvard. *OiYan A. Poon, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Chair: *Joseph Sturm, Pennsylvania State University*

Discussant: *Jaweed Kaleem, Los Angeles Times*

52.037. From Awareness to Action: Educators in Solidarity with Undocumented Communities.

Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Symposium

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 6; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Navigating Legal Violence: How Educators Support Undocumented Students Across Local Contexts. *Daysi X. Diaz-Strong, University of Illinois at Chicago*

"They took my mom to a detention center...": Latinx teachers at the intersection of their families and their student's lives.

Timothy Monreal, University at Buffalo - SUNY

Educating in the Shadow of Illegality: Care, Courage, and Collective Transformation with Undocumented Students.

Blanca Elizabeth Vega, Montclair State University

A Restorative Circle for Educators: Processing Youth Protesting ICE Abductions, Racial Profiling, & Violence.

Oscar Navarro, California State University - Long Beach

Chair: *Christian A. Bracho, California State University - Long Beach*

Discussant: *Arturo Anaya Servin, University of San Diego*

52.038. More than Numbers: The Emotional Labor of Mathematics.

Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 7; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Facing uncertainties in pedagogical responsibility: A math teacher's experience navigating narratives of belonging.

Amanda Coviello, University of Wisconsin - Madison

Veteran Teachers Navigating Traditional and Reform-Oriented Mathematics Experiences, Beliefs, and Tensions. *Kayla Sutcliffe, University of Florida*

Teaching as a Calling: Why Early-Career Math Teachers Stay.

Cristina Runnalls, California State Polytechnic University - Pomona

What a Shame: Thinking Teacher Education, Mathematics, and "Productive Disposition" Through a Politics of Emotion.

Susan Ophelia Cannon, University of Georgia; Kelly

Dollarhide, University of Georgia; Kate O'Brien,

Manchester Metropolitan University; Saniye Nur Ergan, Ordu University

Cross-Country Variation in Mathematics Teachers'

Occupational Well-Being Dimensions: Evidence From PISA

2022. *Mi Jin Park, Graduate Center - CUNY; Bixi Zhang, Graduate Center - CUNY*

Chair: *Amanda Coviello, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Discussant: *Lybrya Kebreab, California State University - Pomona*

52.039. Reclaiming Possibility: Educators Building Learning Futures with Culture, Care, and Play.

Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Symposium

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 2; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Pedagogía de la Ternura: Educators' Visions of Holistic and Dignified Learning with Tzotzil Children. *Karlena Diane*

Ochoa, California State University - Fullerton; Susana

Beltran-Grimm, Portland State University; Jessica Huancacuri, New York University; María Soledad Cecilia Jiménez Melo, Yo'on ixim: Corazón de Maíz; Francisco Armando Ponce Leon, Yo'on ixim: Corazón de Maíz; Yolanda Velazquez Rodriguez, Yo'on ixim: Corazón de Maíz; Alma Lucero Sanchez Hernandez, Yo'on ixim: Corazón de Maíz; Gabrielle Elizabeth Bernal, California State University - Monterey Bay

Culturally Rooted Adaptations of BLINDED PROGRAM in Indigenous Oaxaca: Educators' Insights from Implementation and Reimagining. *TERESITA MERINO, University of California - Irvine; Vanessa Noemy Bermudez, University of California - Irvine; Andres Sebastian Bustamante, University of California - Irvine*

BLINDED PROGRAM in Schools: Teacher-Identified Opportunities for Computational Thinking in Play. *Leiny Yesenia Garcia, Duke University; Jessica Blake-West, Boston College; June Ahn, University of California - Irvine; Andres Sebastian Bustamante, University of California - Irvine*

Educators' Beliefs About Supporting Students With Disabilities as They Transition to Adulthood. *LuEttaMae Lawrence, Utah State University; Stephen Kwiatek, Utah State University; Malin Scharmann, Utah State University*

Chair: *TERESITA MERINO, University of California - Irvine*

Discussant: *Vanessa Noemy Bermudez, University of California - Irvine*

52.040. Rewriting the Narrative: Justice-Centered Professional Learning to Transform Literacy, Language, & Pedagogy. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 9; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Disrupting Deficit Thinking: Reinvigorating Literacy Culture Through Community-Centered Pedagogy. *Jhanae Wingfield, Rutgers University - Newark*

"I Love This Part!": Teachers in Aotearoa New Zealand Collaborating to See Writing and Writers Differently. *Tanya Gray, University of Waikato; Jessica Cira Rubin, University of Waikato*

Language as a Lens: Centering Multilingual Students and Writing in Collaborative, Inquiry-based Teacher Professional Learning. *Alex M. Gurn, Rockman et al Cooperative; Adam R. Moylan, Rockman et al*

"This Ain't a Time Where the Usual is Suitable": A Hip Hop (W)righting, Fugitive Approach to Justice-oriented Professional Development for In-Service Teachers. *H. Bernard Hall, Drexel University; Michele DeVirgilio, Herricks School District; Kareem Edouard, Drexel University; Mariaelois Carambo, Drexel University*

Chair: *Randall M Varner, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*

Discussant: *Benita R. Brooks, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*

52.041. This is How We Do It: Educating Resilient Teacher Educators for Real World Teachers. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 1; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

A Tripod Approach to Language Teacher Educator Well-Being: Intersections of Autonomy, Self-Efficacy, and Resilience. *Nihat Polat, University of Maryland; Jiaxuan Zong, University of Maryland*

Knowledge and Practice in Teacher Educator Preparation: A Systematic Review of Literature. *Brandon M. Butler, Old Dominion University; Jennifer Jacobs, University of South Florida; Diane Yendol-Hoppey, University of North Florida*

Preparing Justice-Oriented Educators in Polarized Contexts: Cross-State Analysis of Teacher Educators as Street-Level Bureaucrats. *Noa Rein, Boston College; Emilie Mitescu Reagan, Claremont Graduate University; Rachel Roegman, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Geyong Zhang, Boston College*

The Paradox of the Preparation-Practice Divide: The (Ir) Relevance of Teacher Education. *Brian R. Sevier, California State University - Channel Islands; Toni M. Williams, University of South Carolina; Christina M. Tschida, Appalachian State University*

Chair: *A. Lin Goodwin, Boston College*

52.042. Towards Youth Participatory Teacher Education. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Atrium III; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

From Adolescent Development to Critical Youth Studies: An Epistemological Repositioning of "Youth" in Teacher Education. *Robert Petrone, University of Missouri*

"We're Making Other People's Future Educations Better": Youth Transforming Teacher Learning Through YPTE Pedagogies. *Acelynn C. Perkins, University of Colorado - Boulder; Daniela Harton, University of Colorado - Boulder; Laura Meinzen, University of Colorado - Boulder; Andrew J. Schiera, University of Colorado - Boulder*

Read the Room: Engaging Youth Leadership and Intergenerational Collaboration in Professional Development for K-12 Teachers. *Lauren Leigh Kelly, Rutgers University*

Pausing to Co-investigate Practice: Democratizing Teacher Education by Centering Youth Voices. *Andrew del Calvo, Rutgers University - New Brunswick; Andrew J. Schiera, University of Colorado - Boulder*

Chairs: *Andrew del Calvo, Rutgers University - New Brunswick; Andrew J. Schiera, University of Colorado - Boulder*

Discussant: *Yolanda Sealey-Ruiz, Teachers College, Columbia University*

52.043. Unforgetting to Imagine Otherwise: Methodological Multiplicity in Teaching and Teacher Education.

Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 8; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Learning from Abuela: La Chakra as a Methodology for Teacher Education Ecosystems. *Jessica Velez Tello, Brooklyn College - CUNY*

Using photovoice as a teaching tool to foster culturally responsive teaching of pre-service teachers in special education. *Sung Hee Lee, California State University - Fullerton; Rosalinda Larios, California State University - Fullerton; Jacqueline Valencia, California State University - Fullerton; Benikia Kressler, California State University - Fullerton*

“Mélange of Pronouns”: A Trans Embodied Experience in Teacher Education. *Nora Aboali, Hunter College - CUNY*

Investigating the Heterogeneous Effects of Teacher Responsiveness and Sensitivity: A Multi-Group SEM Approach. *Chenchen Lu, Purdue University; Chrystal S. Johnson, Purdue University*

Chair: *Evangela Q. Oates, University of Minnesota*

Discussant: *Jessica N. Hiltabidel, George Mason University*

52.044. Money Matters: Finance, Markets, and Equity in School Choice Systems. Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 10; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Unforgetting the Past, Imagining the Future: A Machine Learning Analysis of Virginia School Finance Patterns. *Luke Parker, Virginia Commonwealth University*

Charter Expansion and the Public Good: A Longitudinal Enrollment and Fiscal Analysis in Texas. *David E. DeMatthews, University of Texas at Austin; Jinseok Shin, University of Texas at Austin; Pedro Reyes, University of Texas at Austin; Torri Danny Hart, University of Texas at Austin; Laura Torres, The University of Texas at Austin*

Missing School, Missing Funds: How Attendance-based Funding Impacts Fiscal Equity in Texas. *Blake DeVante Marlowe, University of Texas at Austin*

Drawing on Data, Proposals, or Expertise? Administrators' Rationales When Allocating Resources. *Denise Demski, Ruhr-Universität Bochum; Gabriele Bellenberg, Ruhr University Bochum; Sarah Eiden, Ruhr University Bochum*

Characteristics of Mergers and Acquisitions in the Education Services Sector: A Social Network Analysis (2017-2024). *Shiqi Wu, University of California - Los Angeles; Bradley Curs, University of Missouri; Ozan Jaquette, University of California - Los Angeles*

Chair: *Maria Guajardo, Soka University*

Discussant: *Matthew S. McCluskey, University of Vermont*

SIG Sessions

52.045. Academic Outcomes Shaped by Home and School Experiences. SIG-Adolescence and Youth Development;

Paper Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 301A; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Educational Roles and Identity Formation of Adolescent Firstborns in Chinese Large-Gap Families. *珂珂 王, East China Normal University*

From Home to School During COVID-19: Between- and Within-Person Dynamics of Learning Engagement and Psychological Distress Among Chinese Secondary Students. *NA FU, Beijing Normal University; Xiaochen Xie, The University of North Carolina at Greensboro*

Impact of Social Integration and Individual Traits on Grade Retention: Analysis for U.S. 15-Year-Olds. *Lina Shu, Texas A&M University; Yiming Zhu, Texas A&M University; Xuan Zhou, Texas State University*

School Attendance and Reasons for Missing School Vary by Sense of Belonging. *Tai Tri Do, University of Minnesota; Michael C. Rodriguez, University of Minnesota*

Starting Early: Integrated Student Support and the Long-Term Reduction in School Suspensions. *Xiaohan Qian, Boston College; Haibin Jiang, Boston College*

Chair: *Laura Fittz Parks, Fort Lewis College*

52.046. Social and Emotional Learning of Diverse Youth. SIG-Adolescence and Youth Development; Paper Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 301B; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Comparison of Adolescent SEL Attributes Before, During, and After COVID-19 School Closures. *Summer Blount, Wingate University*

Linking Growth Mind-Set to Social-Emotional Skills Among Chinese Students: A Structural Equation Model Examination. *Jinpeng Niu, Southwest University*

Longitudinal Associations between Social-Emotional Characteristics and Educational and Well-Being Outcomes in Adolescents. *Yi-jhen Wu, TU Dortmund University; Michael Becker, Technische Universität Dortmund; Julia Tetzner, Humboldt University of Berlin*

Motivational Pathways to Cyberhate Among Ukrainian Adolescents: The Role of Revenge and Proactive Motivation. *Julia Levin, University of Hamburg*

The Impact of the 21st-Century Afterschool Program on Students' Behavior and Social Skills. *Akua Anyei Obeng, Harris County Department of Education; Yolanda Pyrtle, Harris County Department of Education; Likita Durden-*

Holmes, Harris County Department of Education
Chair: Hua Luo, Florida State University

52.047. Analyzing Large Scale Data Systems: Methodology and Implications for Practice. SIG-Advanced Studies of National Databases; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum E;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Machine Learning with Explainable AI: Handling Imbalanced Panel Data through Resampling Techniques. *Yeheun Baek, Chungnam National University; Hyewon Chung, Chungnam National University*

On Education Miracles in General (and those in Mississippi in Particular). *Daniel H. Robinson, University of Texas - Arlington; Howard Wainer, Independent; Irina Grabovsky, National Board of Medical Examiners*

Staying Power: How Principals Impact Special Educator Career Intentions. *Danielle Jeamite, University of Florida; Maria Virginia Giani, University of Florida; Christopher Redding, University of Florida; Walter L. Leite, University of Florida*

Chair: *Ya-Chi Hung, University of Southern California*

52.048. Unforgetting Ethnic Studies' Radical Roots when Developing Curriculum on Asian Americans and Pacific Islanders. SIG-Asian Americans and Pacific Islanders in Education and Research; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 506;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Radical Ethnic Studies Pedagogy and Developing Principled Curriculum. *Allyson Tintiangco-Cubales, San Francisco State University; Arlene S. Daus-Magbual, San Francisco State University*

Filipino Farmworkers: Did they Achieve Justice? *Lauren Arzaga Daus, University of California - Los Angeles; Aldrich Limpin Sabac, Stockton Unified School District; Rod Daus-Magbual, Pin@y Educational Partnerships*

Teaching Pacific Islander Frameworks and Futures. *Levalasi Loi-On, San Francisco State University; Jeremiah Cho Sataraka, California State University - Bakersfield*

Underrepresented Asian Americans: How to create curriculum for teachers who may know nothing about us. *Maharaj Desai, California State University - East Bay; Cheralen Arroyo Valdez, University of California - Santa Cruz; Asra Ziauddin*

Unforgetting the Purpose of Ethnic Studies: Teaching about the Strike, Asian Americans as Activists, and Solidarity. *Jocyl Sacramento, California State University - East Bay; Karmela Herrera, Teachers College, Columbia University; Artnelson Concordia, Santa Barbara Unified School District; Giselle Dejamco Cunanan, Gonzaga University*

Chair: *Edward R. Curammeng, California State University - Dominguez Hills*

Discussant: *Karen Umamoto, University of California - Los Angeles*

52.049. (Re)shaping Multilingual Learners' Schooling: Educators as Translators of Language Policy. SIG-Bilingual Education Research; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 501C;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Beyond Compliance: Educators as Policy Interpreters in the Waiving of English Learner Services. *Janette Dalila Avelar, University of Oregon*

(Re)negotiating language credits: A critical policy analysis of Oregon's Access to Linguistic Inclusion law. *Jaclyn B. Bovee, Oregon State University*

Flexibility as language allocation policy in bilingual education: Equity for all or for some? *Daniel Garzon, California State University - Los Angeles*

Chairs: *Janette Dalila Avelar, University of Oregon; Jaclyn B. Bovee, Oregon State University*

Discussant: *Ester J. de Jong, University of Colorado - Denver*

52.050. Neuroscience, AI, and Emotion in Education: Bridging Cognitive and Social Development. SIG-Brain, Neurosciences and Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Atrium I;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

AI-Enhanced Mathematics Instruction and Executive Function Gains in Eighth-Grade Learners. *Şeyma Sultan Uçar, Middle East Technical University; Gokce Gokalp, Middle East Technical University*

Autistic symptom severity differentially relates to neural entropy and child-parent social behavior during math processing. *Analia Marzoratti, University of Virginia; Megan Liu, Massachusetts General Hospital; Emily Fuhrmann, University of Virginia; Rose Nevill, University of Virginia; Kevin Pelphrey, University of Virginia; Meghan Puglia, University of Virginia; Tanya Evans, University of Virginia*

Neural Narratives: The Cognitive Cost of Curriculum and Neural Bias Regulation in U.S. History Education. *Tanishia Lavette Williams, Brandeis University*

Prior Knowledge Shapes Individualized Academic Emotion Profiles: Behavioral and Neural Evidence. *Xingda Li, Tsinghua University; Dan Zhang, Tsinghua University; Jingjing Chen, Tsinghua University*

Chair: *Jingjing Chen, Tsinghua University*

52.051. Career Development Opportunities Today and Tomorrow: Toward Equity and Opportunity. SIG-Career & Technical Education and Workplace Learning; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 3;

9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Opportunity and Access: Availability of Career Development Opportunities in Baltimore City Public Schools. *Jay Plasman, The Ohio State University; Tarsha I. Herelle, Johns Hopkins University; Rachel E. Durham, Notre Dame of Maryland University; Marcia H. Davis, Johns Hopkins University; Martha Abele Mac Iver, Johns Hopkins University; Rooppreet Sohal-Bagri, The Ohio State University; Al Passarella, Johns Hopkins University; Daniel Princiotta, Johns Hopkins University*

Career Development Opportunities in Washington, DC Public Schools. *Dara Zeehandelaar Shaw, Urban Institute; Chelsea Coffin, D.C. Policy Center; Rebecca Anne Johnson, New York City Department of Education*

Opportunity and Constraint: Program Design and Student Choice in High School Career and Technical Education. *Benjamin W. Dalton, RTI International; Sandra Staklis, RTI International; Natassia Rodriguez Ott, RTI International; Jill Pierce, Research Triangle Institute; Terri Dempsey, RTI International*

Geographic Access and Racial/Ethnic Representation in Chicago Public Schools CTE Pathways. *Amy E. Arneson, UChicago Consortium on School Research; Laura Davis, UChicago Consortium on School Research; Sarah E. Cashdollar, University of Illinois System; Kaitlyn Franklin, University of Chicago; Raisa Blazquez, Illinois Workforce and Education Research Collaborative; Gertrude Bakalus, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Mahnoor Arif, University of Chicago*

Navigating Pathways: Examining CTE and Linked Learning in LAUSD. *Kyra Caspary, Lauren Cassidy, SRI International; Thomas Kelley-Kemple, Harvard University; Jenna Rush, SRI International; Miya Tamiko Warner, SRI International*

Chair: *Sarah E. Cashdollar, University of Illinois System*

Discussant: *Katherine Hughes, EdWordian, LLC*

52.052. Reimagining Assessment as a Learning Process: Student Voice, Classroom Practice, and Data Analytics.

SIG-Classroom Assessment; Paper Session
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Echo Park; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Centering Student Voice in Science Assessment through Leveraging Student Experience Data. *Cari F. Herrmann-Abell, BSCS Science Learning; Clarissa de Oliveira Deverel-Rico, BSCS Science Learning; Jeffrey Snowden, BSCS Science Learning; Andy Brubaker, BSCS Science Learning; Melissa R. Campanella, University of Colorado - Boulder; Jean Flanagan, BSCS Science Learning; Dennis Michael Lee, BSCS Science Learning; Patricia Olson, BSCS Science Learning; Christopher D. Wilson, Biological Sciences Curriculum Study*

Exploring Student Motivation and Engagement in Self-

Assessment: An Expectancy-Value Theory Perspective. *Deborah G. Fabiyi, Washington State University; Oluyemisi Ajoke Oloniyo, Washington State University; Deborah Moyaki, University of Georgia; Nathaniel Hunsu, University of Georgia*

An approximate replication of reassessing the relationship between classroom tasks and environment in EFL Classrooms. *He Yang, City University of Macao; Liying Cheng, City University of Macao; Yiran Miao, Chengdu University of Information Technology; Sihui Yu, City University of Macao*

Expanding Assessment for Targeted Literacy Supports: The Role of Social-Emotional Learning and Creativity. *Emily Johns-O'Leary, University of Colorado - Boulder*

Systematic Review of Process Data Analytics in K-12 Education. *Yaxuan Yang, University of Georgia; Ruiping Huang, University of Illinois at Chicago; Yue Yin, University of Illinois at Chicago; Xiaoming Zhai, University of Georgia*

Chair: *Sue Brookhart, Duquesne University*

Discussant: *Nathan H. Rickey, Queen's University - Kingston*

52.053. Imagining Liberatory Futures: Pedagogical Resistance in the Past, Present, and Future through Abolitionist Place-Based Methods. SIG-Critical Educators for Social Justice; Workshop

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304C; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Is it in your 𐄂 / Jai?: Embodied Knowledge and Participatory Arts-Based Co-Learning and Co-Creation. *Sunisa Nuonsy, Graduate Center - CUNY*

What to Do When the Streetlights Go Out: Jet Magazine as Archival Homeplace. *Cornie Belser, CUNY Graduate Center*

Place Matters: Mapping Stories and Resisting Erasure through Testimonio and Counter-Mapping. *Michelle R. Ochoa, Graduate Center - CUNY*

LGBTQIA+ Students and Teachers Co-Creating Oral Histories From the Future That Move People To Action. *Natalie Willens, Graduate Center - CUNY*

Interpreting Our Past Freedom Dreams for the Present and Future. *Jennifer Queenan*

Chair: *Michelle R. Ochoa, Graduate Center - CUNY*

52.054. (Re)imagining Education Research Through Muslim Perspectives. SIG-Critical Muslim Education Research; Symposium

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304B; 9:45-11:15am

Chair: *Noor Ali, Northeastern University*

Participants: *Gholnecsar Gholdy Muhammad, University of Illinois at Chicago; Muhammad Khalifa, The Ohio State University; Miriam Deborah Ezzani, Texas Christian University*

52.055. Understanding Educational Practitioner Data Use.

SIG-Data-Driven Decision Making in Education; Paper Session

InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Los Feliz; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Laying Groundwork for a Data Culture: A Case Study. *Julie W. Dallavis, University of Notre Dame; Mary Frances Jones, University of Notre Dame*

Developing and Validating a Practitioner Toolkit to Support Collaborative Data Inquiry. *Candice Bocala, Harvard University; Lindsay Brown, New York University; Selin Capan, SRI International; Paul Burkander, SRI International; Katrina Laguarda, SRI International; Kerry Schellenberger, SRI International*

Changing Teacher's Data Driven Approaches: The DELP-Mixed-Methods Analysis. *Fay S. Quiroz, University of Wyoming*

A Systematic Review of Data-Based Decision-Making Training for Pre-service Teachers. *Eunji Kong, University of Oregon; Yitong Jiang; Wenjing Bao, University of Oregon; Stephanie Shire, University of Oregon*

Chair: *Kevin Fortner, Georgia State University*

Discussant: *Bo Pei, University of South Florida*

52.056. Surfacing Teacher Learning Needs from the Ground Up: Research-Practice Partnerships to Cultivate Innovative Practices.

SIG-Design and Technology; Symposium

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Santa Barbara C; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Empowering Teachers: A Co-Designed Approach to Innovative Instruction. *Marisol Kevelson, Educational Testing Service; Jamie N. Mikeska, Educational Testing Service; Nancy Grim, Tucson Unified School District; Shreyashi Halder, ETS; Tricia Maxwell, Educational Testing Service*

Responding to Teacher Needs in a Research-practice Partnership. *Josie Melton, Western Washington University; Sarah Voss, Western Washington University; Deborah Hanuscin, Western Washington University*

Establishing a Partnership Between a Rural School and an Urban University to Support Algebra 1 Learning for Students with Learning Disabilities. *Anna Fricano DeJarnette, University of Cincinnati; Casey Hord, University of Cincinnati; David Adams, University of Cincinnati*

Building a Research-Practice Partnership for State-wide Early Math Professional Learning. *Annastasia Purinton, University of Delaware; Lynsey K. Gibbons, University of Delaware*

Creating State-wide Value for High-Quality Mathematics Instruction. *Allison McCulloch, North Carolina State*

University; Catherine Stein Schwartz, East Carolina University; Katherine Mawhinney, Appalachian State University; Michelle L. Stephan, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; P. Holt Wilson, University of North Carolina - Greensboro

Exploring Regional Design Collaboratives as an Implementation Strategy for Equity-focused Science Teacher Learning. *Philip L. Bell, University of Washington; Nancy Price, University of Washington; Ximena Fabiola Gallegos Gutierrez, University of Washington*

Chair: *Marisol Kevelson, Educational Testing Service*

Discussant: *Jenny Bradbury, AERDF*

52.057. Resisting Curriculum as 'Normalizing Text': A 20-Year Retrospective on Disability-Centered Epistemologies in Curriculum Theory.

SIG-Disability Studies in Education; Symposium

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 511AB; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Co-designing Disability-Centered Culturally Sustaining Pedagogies with Community Activists and Youth Scholars. *Amanda L. Miller, Wayne State University; Saili S. Kulkarni, San Jose State University; Emily A. Nusbaum, University of California - Berkeley; Ajya Wilson, Wayne County Community College; Holly Pearson, Massachusetts Commission for the Deaf and Hard of Hearing; Brianna J Dickens, Syracuse University*

Composing Disabled Histories and Futures: A Participatory Place Conscious Approach to Disability History Education. *Molly Elizabeth Siuty, Temple University; Naomi Fair, Rutgers University - Camden*

Crippling Culturally Sustaining Pedagogies as a Curricular Practice: Centering Disabled Youth in Transformative Praxis. *Sarah Arvey Tov, University of Washington*

Pedagogical Resistance in Crip Cyberspace: A Study of Crip Liberatory Pedagogy within Online Neurodivergent Community. *Andrea F. Parente, Temple University; Isabella Ramirez de Arellano, Temple University*

Chairs: *Molly Elizabeth Siuty, Temple University; Naomi Fair, Rutgers University - Camden*

Discussant: *Nirmala Erevelles, University of Alabama*

52.058. Evidence-Based Practice for Early STEM Teaching and Learning: Diverse Adult Roles and Contexts.

SIG-Early Education and Child Development; Symposium

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Georgia I; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Impact of Early STEM Professional Training on Pre-Service Teachers' STEM Understanding and Teaching Self-Efficacy. *Keting Chen, California State University - San Bernardino; Hyeungok Kang, California State University - San Bernardino; Lisa Looney, California State University - San*

Bernardino; Cade Parker, California State University- San Bernardino; Angie Arriaga Cazares, California State University - San Bernardino

The Effectiveness of Hands-on Number Talks on Teacher Candidates' Mathematics Teaching Efficacy and Attitudes. *Shinho Kim, Framingham State University; Shin Ae Han, University of Hawai'i at Manoa; SungEun Min, Kutztown University of Pennsylvania; Jonga Lee, Sungkyunkwan University*

Effect of The Elaborative Conversation Strategies Intervention on Parent-Child Science Talk. *Yao Yao, University of Nebraska - Lincoln; Soo-Young Hong, University of Nebraska-Lincoln*

Promoting Social-Emotional Learning through Robot-Based Programming Activities in Early Childhood Education: A Systematic Review. *Hyeungok Kang, California State University - San Bernardino; Eun Hye Grace Ko, Texas A&M University; Min Sun Kim, Franklin University; Hye Ryung Won, Slippery Rock University of Pennsylvania; Sehyun Yun, Ball State University*

Chair: *Keting Chen, California State University - San Bernardino*

Discussant: *Angela Stone-MacDonald, California State University - San Bernardino*

52.059. Preparing and supporting teachers for climate and sustainability education. SIG-Environmental Education; Paper Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 401; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Designing Effective Climate Change Education Professional Development: Overcoming Challenges and Seizing Opportunities for K-12 Teachers. *Merav Hayak, Columbia University; Achva Academic College; Ben-Gurion University of the Negev; Oren Pizmony-Levy, Teachers College, Columbia University; Jooyoung Jeon, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Changing Minds, Building Capacity: Evaluating the Impact of Climate Changed Education Professional Development on Teachers. *Oren Pizmony-Levy, Teachers College, Columbia University; Christina Ann Torres, Teachers College, Columbia University; Noa Urbach, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Teacher Candidates' Sensemaking of Sustainable Energy Education: Multi-Case Study in Germany, India, and the US. *Arya Karumanthra, Indiana University; Gayle A. Buck, Indiana University; Sandra Sprenger, Universität Hamburg; Neli Heidari, University of Hamburg; Patricia K. Kubow, Indiana University*

Integrating Sustainability in U.S. Teacher Preparation: A Systematic Review of Empirical and Conceptual Literature (2015–2025). *Peter O Oyewole, Kent State University*

Discussant: *Isaac B. Bolaji, Kent State University*

52.060. Learning from “failure”: Exploring challenges in unsuccessful research-practice partnerships. SIG-Improvement Science in Education; Symposium
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Los Cerritos; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

From initiation to dissolution: Learning from the unsuccessful launch of networked improvement. *Jennifer Karnopp, San Diego State University; Chad Lochmiller, Indiana University*

Between Transaction and Collaboration: Struggles in the Boundary Zone of a Fizzled-Out Research-Practice Partnership. *Elizabeth Zumpe, University of Oklahoma; Peter Piazza, University of Massachusetts - Amherst; Katherine Ashton, University of Oklahoma*

When foundations shake: Navigating structural and political fragility in a Chilean Research Practice Partnership (RPP). *Bárbara Zoro, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Valparaíso; Fernanda Goni, Universidad de Chile*

"Without us there is no project": Drifting away in an RPP as a risk of failure, and how to be on track again. *Florencia Gomez Zaccarelli, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile; Javiera Marfán, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile; Susana Mendive, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile*

Shifting the Goalposts: Evolving Conceptualizations of Failure and Success in Research Practice Partnerships. *Megan Duff, UNC Chapel Hill; Joshua L. Glazer, The George Washington University; Matthew Shirrell, The George Washington University*

Chair: *Elizabeth Zumpe, University of Oklahoma*

Discussant: *Maxwell Yurkofsky, Radford University*

52.061. Integrating AI in Pre-service Teacher Education. SIG-Instructional Technology; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Level 2, Echo Park; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Preservice Teachers' Prompting Practices and Decision-Making in Using Generative Artificial Intelligence. *Yin Hong Cheah, University of Idaho; Hsiao-Ping Hsu, Dublin City University; Jingru Lu, University of Idaho; Raghad Faisal Alsaka, University of Idaho*

From Planning to Practice: AI-Supported Lesson Internalization and Pre-service Teacher Self-Efficacy in Mixed Reality Settings. *Nelson Cubas, University of Houston; Susie Gronseth, University of Houston*

Pre-Service Teachers and Generative AI: Perceptions, Professional Impacts, and Pedagogical Readiness. *Gulbahar Yilmaz, Michigan State University; Aman Yadav, Michigan State University*

Relationship Between Pre-Service Teachers' Perceived Competencies, Affective Dispositions, and Readiness to Integrate Artificial Intelligence. *Ayesha Sadaf, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Daniel Maxwell, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Heiko Holz, Ludwigsburg University of Education*

Title: "ChatGPT Was Okay, But I Needed My Peer": Preservice Teachers' Experiences with AI and Human Feedback." *Gui Ying Annie Yang-Heim, Illinois State University; Xi Lin, East Carolina University*

52.062. Thoughts on international education. SIG-International Studies; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 303A;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Financial Strategies Among International Graduate Students in Higher Education. *Bismark Wiafe Bimpong, Ohio University; Ebenezer Takyi-Wadieh, Ohio University; Ebenezer Agorsor, Ohio University*

From Struggling to Balancing: Tracing the Self-Formation of Mainland Chinese Doctoral Student in a Supercomplex Academic Space. *Yabing Liu, Education University of Hong Kong; Anatoly Oleksiyenko, The Education University of Hong Kong; Weiyang Xiong, Education University of Hong Kong*

Topic Modeling of Research Paradigms: A Comprehensive Review of Research on International Students. *YoungHoon Koh, The University of Arizona; Seongjin Park, Speak*

Chair: *Sabahet S. Bruncaj, United Arab Emirates University*

52.063. 12th Annual Language and Social Processes Mentoring Session. SIG-Language and Social Processes; Workshop
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 403A;
9:45-11:15am

Chairs: *Tairan Qiu, Stanford University; Jungmin Kwon, Michigan State University; Faythe Beauchemin, Boston College*

Participants: *Zhongfeng Tian, Rutgers University - Newark; Robert Jean LeBlanc, University of Lethbridge; Kevin M. Wong, Pepperdine University; Matt DeRoo, Florida International University; Huan Gao, University of Memphis; Karis Michelle Jones, Baylor University; Emily Machado, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Maneka Deanna Brooks, Portland State University; Jon M. Wargo, University of Michigan; Theresa Y. Austin, University of Massachusetts - Amherst; Katie Bernstein, Arizona State University; Chris K. Chang-Bacon, University of Virginia; Wenyang Sun, University of Utah; Cynthia J. Lewis, University of California - Santa Cruz; Angie Zapata, University of Missouri; Audrey Lucero, University of Oregon; Quentin Sedlacek, Southern Methodist University; Audra Skukauskaitė, University of Central Florida; Huseyin Uysal, The Education University of Hong Kong; Lucia Cardenas Curiel, Michigan State University; Cassie J. Brownell, University of Toronto; Hyelin Park, University of Wisconsin-Madison; Salih Mansur, Touro University; Pa Nou Vue, University of California - Berkeley; Juliana Hirn, University of Central Florida; Mingzhu Deng, Georgetown University; Wahyu Kyestiati Sumarno, University of Central Florida; Yifang Xu, Michigan State University; Ashleigh Daher,*

University of Massachusetts - Amherst; Yetunde S. Alabede, Michigan State University; Hye-In Yang, Michigan State University; Li Yong, Boston College; Ming Ming Cheung, Michigan State University; Kyle P. Smith, University of Michigan; Felicity Rhode, Clemson University; Anne Elizabeth O'Brien West, Clemson University; Laxmi Prasad Ojha, Saginaw Valley State University; Marisol Masso, Michigan State University; Ashley Houston-King, Boston University; Pyeongeun Kim, Michigan State University; Morgan Marie King, Clemson University; Deepshikha Banerjee, Boston College; Valerie Ann Hammer, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Seungwoo Hwang, Michigan State University; Luqing Zang, Slippery Rock University of Pennsylvania; Junling Zhu, University of Massachusetts - Amherst; Lexi Woodward, University of Arkansas; Juyeon Yoo, Ball State University; Brenda Luo, Boston College; Eunjin Cho, University of Massachusetts - Amherst; Yonghui Wang, University of Houston; Yi Zhang, University of Houston

Presenters: *Cati V. de los Rios, University of California - Berkeley; Maria Paula Ghiso, Teachers College, Columbia University; Shondel J. Nero, New York University; Antero Garcia, Stanford University*

52.064. Futuring through Form: Multimodal Scholarship and Public Engagement. SIG-Media, Culture, and Learning;
Symposium

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum I;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Re/Forming Academic Publication Through Collective Magazine Production. *Haeny S. Yoon, Teachers College, Columbia University; Lucius Von Joo, Teachers College, Columbia University; Lalitha Vasudevan, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Podcasts and Public Voice. *Joseph Riina-Ferrie, Teachers College, Columbia University; Jacqueline A. Simmons, Teachers College, Columbia University; Sarah M. Gerth van den Berg, Teachers College, Columbia University; Nathan Holbert, Teachers College, Columbia University; OreOluwa Badaki, Teachers College, Columbia University; Azsanee Truss, University of Pennsylvania; Sonali Rajan, National Development and Research Institutes, Inc.*

Imagining Otherwise: Academic Communication as Utopian Practice. *Ioana Literat, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Chair: *Haeny S. Yoon, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Discussant: *Amy Noelle Parks, Michigan State University*

52.065. Multilingualism, Identity, and Belonging. SIG-Multicultural/Multiethnic Education: Theory, Research and Practice; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Georgia II;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

What Teachers Say They Need: Mapping Multilingual & Multicultural Stances for Professional Development Using PISA 2022. *Ruoyi Zhang, Brooklyn RISE Charter School; Jianing Li, Fordham University*

Language, Identity, and Belonging Among Latinx Diaspora Youth in Spain. *Eric Ruiz Bybee, Brigham Young University*

Sticky Belonging at the Intersection: Experiences of One Bilingual Immigrant Teacher Candidate with Dis/ability.

Jihea Maddamsetti, Old Dominion University

Chair: *Jennifer M. Bondy, Arizona State University*

Discussant: *Zheng Ma, University of Toronto - OISE*

52.066. Expanding Possibilities: Equity, Identity, and Culture in Out-of-School Time Spaces. SIG-Out-of-School Time;

Paper Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 501B; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Beyond the Classroom: Black Girls' Embodied Literacies and Cultural Preservation Through Majorette Dance. *Tempestt S. Johnson, University of South Carolina*

Confronting History in California 4-H: Organizational Change Strategies for Advancing Access and Equity. *Kaitlyn Murray, University of California 4-H Youth Development Program; Liliana Vega, University of California 4-H Youth Development Program; Stepha Velednitsky, University of California*

Our Uniqueness in Reading (O.U.R.) Afterschool Book Club. *Wyletta S. Gamble-Lomax, Coppin State University*

Teaching Youth to Create Ensembles for Their Own Development: A Performance-Based Approach to Out-of-School Time Practice. *Carrie L. Lobman, Rutgers University; Bonny L. Gildin, All Stars Project Inc.*

Undoing Acts of Historical Erasure: Breaking from Dominant Frames of White Wupremacy as Civic Engagement. *Katie Headrick Taylor, University of Washington; Audrey Harris, University of Washington*

Discussant: *Ishmael Miller, Arizona State University*

52.067. Exploring Various Teaching and Learning Methods of Mathematics Topics. SIG-Research in Mathematics

Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum A; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Assessing Students' Understanding of Average Through Problem Posing: A Focus on the Impact of Prompts. *Jinfa Cai, University of Delaware; Jia Pang, Yangzhou University; suanrong Chen, Yangzhou University*

Exploring Early Forms of Perceptual Subitizing, Conceptual Subitizing, and Number Structuring. *Beth Loveday MacDonald, Illinois State University; Laura Bofferding, Purdue University; Doris Fulwider, Purdue University; Yi*

Zhu, Purdue University; Sanhei Nhor, Illinois State University

"I Don't Even Want to Touch Quadratics": How Mathematics Content Structures Teachers' Ethical Decision-making.

Grace A. Chen, New York University; Nurdan Turan, New York University; Sarah C. Radke, Concord Consortium;

Anne S. Burgunder, New York University; Jasmine Y. Ma, New York University

Preservice Teachers' Fractional Reasoning and Their Intentions to Use a Dynamic Digital Tool: A Mixed-Methods Study

Using FracTopia. *Mi Yeon Lee, Arizona State University; Sheunghyun Yeo, Daegu National University of Education;*

Jinam Hwang, Yongjung Elementary School

Teachers' Geometric Reasoning with Invariant Features of Change in a Dynamic Environment. *Gal Gili Nagar,*

University of Massachusetts - Dartmouth

Chair: *Arpana Manjunath, University of Houston*

Discussant: *Sarah A. van Ingen Lauer, University of South Florida*

52.068. AI in Literacy Education: Imagining the Future While Building on Proven Practices. SIG-Research in Reading

and Literacy; Symposium

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Beaudry A; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Simplifying Middle-Grade Texts Using AI Extensions: Impacts on Text Vocabulary and Cohesion. *Heidi Anne E. Mesmer, Virginia Tech; Elfrieda H. Hiebert, TextProject*

Benchmarking Large Language Models on Generating Expository Elementary Science Text. *Guy Trainin, University of Nebraska - Lincoln; Azadeh Hassani, University of Nebraska - Lincoln; Fatemeh Ashrafabadi,, University of Nebraska - Lincoln; Qizhen Deng, Boise State University*

AI-Generated Decodable Texts: Problems, Promise, and Directions Supporting Beginning Reading Objectives. *Laura S. Tortorelli, Michigan State University; John Z. Strong, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Tanya M. Christ, East Carolina University*

Towards Scalable Vocabulary Assessment: Pilot Evidence for Reliable AI-Generated Items. *Joshua Fahey Lawrence, University of Oslo; Rebecca Silverman, Stanford University; Jason D. Yeatman, Stanford University; Åste Hagen, University of Oslo; Jasmine Tran, University of California - Irvine*

Chair: *Elfrieda H. Hiebert, TextProject*

Discussant: *Elfrieda H. Hiebert, TextProject*

52.069. Heterogeneity in Educational Intervention Fadeout and Long-run Mechanisms: Three Analyses of Block-Level Impact Patterns. SIG-Research on Evaluation;

Symposium

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Beaudry B; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Re-Examining the Head Start Impact Study: Impact Persistence and the Counterfactual Condition. *Caroline Botvin, Columbia University; Emma Hart, Boston College; Drew Bailey, University of California - Irvine; Tyler Watts, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Using Experimental Variation to Examine the Co-Development of Cognitive and Social-emotional Skills in Early Childhood. *Emma Hart, Boston College; Caroline Botvin, Columbia University; Drew Bailey, University of California - Irvine; Tyler Watts, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Exploring Cognitive and Social-Emotional Impact Patterns in a Randomized Controlled Trial of Math Tutoring. *Siling Guo, University of California - Irvine; Sarah R. Powell, University of Texas at Austin; Emma Hart, Boston College; Caroline Botvin, Columbia University; Xin Lin, University of Macau; Tyler Watts, Teachers College, Columbia University; Drew Bailey, University of California - Irvine*

Chair: *Emma Hart, Boston College*

Discussant: *Joshua Baer Gilbert, Harvard University*

52.070. Positionality and Research Use in Educational Policy and Practice: Toward Evidence-Informed Decisions.

SIG-Research Use; Structured Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 515B;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

1. District Administrator Positionality in Knowledge Mobilization: Boundary Spanning in Ontario's Educational Context (Poster 1). *Sofia Malik, University of Texas at Austin; Muhammad A Shah, Lusail University, Qatar*
2. From Teacher to Politician: How State Education Agency Content Coordinators Navigate Politics (Poster 2). *Emily M. Hodge, Virginia Commonwealth University; Serena J. Salloum, Ball State University; Susanna Latham Benko, Ball State University*
3. Constructing a New Vision for Impactful Research Communication between Academics and Elementary Teachers (Poster 3). *Jessica Rodrigues, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Emily Singell, University of Missouri; Lindsey Mirielli, University of Kansas*
4. The Role of Teachers in Searching and Vetting Evidence to inform Localized Educational Policy (Poster 4). *Mariah Kornbluh, University of Oregon; Sherry Bell, University of Oregon; gabi Garcia, University of Oregon; Raquel Amador, University of Oregon*
5. Braiding Research and Practice: Attending to Power Dynamics and Co-Creating Knowledge to Improve Educational Systems (Poster 5). *Lindsey J. Kaiser, University of Maine; Caitlin Farrell, University of Colorado - Boulder*
6. The riddle of the middle: Understanding how intermediaries promote research use in K-12 education (Poster 6). *Lucas Held, Strategic Communications Consultant; Ece Tekbulut,*

Columbia University

7. The Role of Trust: Intermediaries and Organizational Change within Higher Education Institutions (Poster 7). *Emily Parrott, Thrive Scholars; Travis Heath Olson, Michigan State University; Anna Drake Warshaw, University Innovation Alliance*

Chair: *David R. Garcia, Arizona State University*

Discussant: *Joel R. Malin, Miami University (OH)*

52.071. Reimagining School Effectiveness: Theories, Evidence, and Emerging Paradigms. SIG-School Effectiveness and School Improvement; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Atrium II;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Gendered Staffrooms, Gendered Skills? School Wide Female Teacher Shares and Student Development. *Baeksan Yu, Gwangju National University of Education; Yeseul Doo, University of Chicago*

Causal Effects of Small Class on Students' Social-Emotional and Behavior Outcomes. *Ting Shen, Missouri University of Science & Technology; Spyros Konstantopoulos, Michigan State University*

Development and Validation of an Arts-based Program Impact Scale: An Evidence-based Tool for Public Schools. *Xiaobo Wei, University of South Carolina; Ashlee A. Lewis, University of South Carolina; Dalisha Shingler, University of South Carolina*

Organizational Change Fatigue and Intention to Leave Teaching: International Evidence. *Heather E. Price, Learning Policy Institute*

Using different criteria to measure school effectiveness: Searching for criterion-consistency. *Leonidas Kyriakides, University of Cyprus; Evi Charalambous, University of Cyprus; Demos Michael, University of Cyprus; Panayiotis Antoniou, University of Cyprus*

Chair: *Vanessa Hammler Kenon, University of Texas - San Antonio*

Discussant: *Maria L Lawson-Davenport, Norfolk State University*

52.072. Tensions in Self-Study: Grappling with Boundaries, Relationships, & New Roles. SIG-Self-Study of Teacher Education Practices; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum D; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Crossing Pedagogical Boundaries: A Self-Study of the Transition from Teaching Physics Content to Teaching Early Childhood Science Methods. *Esther Kataate Namakula, Indiana University; Valarie Akerson, Indiana University*
Self-Study of My Teaching in a Survey Course about Meeting the Needs of Diverse Learners. *Amy H. Staples, University of Northern Iowa; Deborah L. Tidwell, University of Northern Iowa*

To ask or not to ask? Delving into the unspoken. *Annette Easley, Aldine Independent School District; Michaelann Kelley, Mount St. Joseph University; Gayle A. Curtis, Texas A&M University; Cheryl J. Craig, Texas A&M University*
A Self-Study of Designing and Teaching an Equity-Centered Classroom Ecology Course in Music Education. *Daniel Taylor, Vanderbilt University*
Support or Sabotage? A Self-Study of How Outside Consultants Shaped a New Urban Leader's Journey. *Mona Beth Zignego, LUMIN Schools*
Chair: *Kelly Lormand, Grand Valley State University*
Discussant: *Monica Taylor, Montclair State University*

52.073. Whose Modes Matter? Creating Robust, Peer-Reviewed Publishing Pathways for Multimodal Scholars. SIG-Semiotics in Education: Signs, Meanings and Multimodality; Working Group Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 501A; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Scoping Peer Reviewed Journals for Supporting Multimodal Publishing in Literacy and Language Education. *Brett Stamm, University of Southern Mississippi; Qianqian Ma, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Katarina N. Silvestri, SUNY - College at Cortland; Aijuan Cun, University of New Mexico*
More Than Words: Publishing Multimodal Research in Multimodal Ways. *Fei Victor Lim, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University*
Nexus Analysis in a Cardigan: Softening Multimodal Edges for the Ivory Tower. *Casey M. Pennington, SUNY Cortland; Amy Walker, Kent State University*
These Aren't Just Decorative: Challenges of Publishing Visuals in Empirical Research. *Julianna E. Lopez Kershen, University of Oklahoma; Kristy Brugar, University of Oklahoma*

Chair: *Katarina N. Silvestri, SUNY - College at Cortland*

52.074. Creating An Agenda For The Future: SEL In Higher Education. SIG-Social and Emotional Learning; Demonstration/Performance
Westin Bonaventure, Level 3, Santa Monica B; 9:45-11:15am

Participant:

Creating An Agenda For The Future: SEL In Higher Education. *Lina Darwich, Lewis & Clark College; Lauren Vega ONeil, Portland State University; Teri Tilley, Portland State University; Deirdre A Hon, University of Portland*

Chair: *Lina Darwich, Lewis & Clark College*

52.075. From Spirit Lynching to Radical Well-Being: Kinship as Resistance to Violence in Higher Education. SIG-Stress, Coping, and Resilience; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 303B; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Naming the Unseen Wounds: Introducing Spirit Lynching as Public Spiritual Violence in Higher Education. *Candice Peters, Appalachian State University*
Kinship as Foundation: Reclaiming Self and Spirit through Sisterhood in the Aftermath of Institutional Violence. *Rosalie Zdzienicka Fanshel, University of California - Berkeley*
Radical Rebuild: Envisioning Structures of Accountability and Well-Being in the Academy. *Raquel Wright-Mair, Rowan University*

Chair: *Jamar Green, University of Kentucky*

Discussant: *Erin Doran, University of Texas - El Paso*

52.076. Reducing Psychological Barriers to Effective Self-Regulated Learning in STEM. SIG-Studying and Self-Regulated Learning; Symposium
Westin Bonaventure, Level 2, Mt. Washington; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Changing the Narrative: Reframing Help-Seeking Boosts Academic Performance Among First-Generation College Students. *Cameron Hecht, University of Rochester; Kali Trzesniewski, University of California - Davis; Elizabeth A. Canning, Washington State University; Evelyn Mandujano, University of California - Davis; Anh Vu, University of Rochester*
The Promise of Mastery-Based Testing for Motivating and Scaffolding Self-Regulated Learning in Gateway STEM Courses. *Michael W. Asher, Carnegie Mellon University; Joshua Hartman, University of California, Riverside; Mark Blaser, Shasta College; Jack Eichler, University of California - Riverside; Paulo Carvalho, Carnegie Mellon University*
The Effects of Multimedia Procrastination-Avoidance Training on STEM Undergraduates' Self-Beliefs, Learning Behaviors, and Achievement. *Matthew L. Bernacki, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Hannah Snyder, Brandeis University; Christy Strong, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Jenifer Utz, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Kathryn Rafferty, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Robert D Plumley, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Vanessa Wanchanit Vongkulluksn, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Akira Miyake, University of Colorado*
Scaling Strategic Resource Use: Evaluating the Translational Effectiveness of the Exam Playbook Intervention. *Patricia Chen, University of Texas at Austin; Luke D. Rutten, University of Texas at Austin; Nathaniel Woznicki, New York University; Yang-Hsin Fan, University of Texas at Austin; Holly A. Derry, University of Michigan; Benjamin T. Hayward, University of Michigan; Erin Murray, University of Michigan; Rebecca L. Matz, University of Michigan; Desmond C. Ong, University of Texas at Austin*
Chair: *Cameron Hecht, University of Rochester*

Discussant: *Andrew C. Butler, Washington University in St. Louis*

52.077. Inquiry as Leadership: A Cross-Boundary Dialogue on Teacher-Led Equity Audits in High-Poverty Schools.

SIG-Teacher as Researcher; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum J;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Uncovering Disparities to Advance Equity: A Middle School Teacher's Inquiry into Representation and Access. *Erin Hunter, Shelby County Schools*

Listening for Equity: Examining Instructional Opportunities in a Rural Elementary School. *Lauren Brascho, University of Alabama - Birmingham*

Identifying Invisible Gaps: A School-Based Audit of Special Education Practices. *Caitlin Thorington, University of Alabama - Birmingham*

Leading Together: A Collaborative Equity Audit of Representation, Access, and School Culture. *Micah Ducre-Toomer, Cobb County School District; Myra Bodrick, Gwinnett County Public Schools*

Chair: *Miyoshi Juergensen, University of Alabama - Birmingham*

Discussants: *Adriana Villavicencio, New York University; Amanda J. Cordova, North Dakota State University; Cailen O'Shea, North Dakota State University*

52.078. Tracing the Attacks on Higher Education from Palestine to Present. SIG-Teachers Work/Teacher Unions; Workshop

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 411 (Theatre); 9:45-11:15am

Chair: *Dana Morrison, West Chester University of Pennsylvania*

Participants: *Denisha Jones, Defending the Early Years; Erin Lee Dyke, Oklahoma State University*

Discussant: *Brianne Kramer, Southern Utah University*

Division and SIG Roundtables

52.079. AERA Roundtable Session Friday 9:45 am; Roundtable Session

52.079-1. The ongoing struggle for educational change after apartheid: Shadows of history, elusive futures (Table 1).

Division A - Administration; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Leading for change in the schools apartheid forgot. *Jonathan David Jansen, Stellenbosch University*

Principals, politics and the pandemic: leading schools in an existential crisis. *Trevor Andre DaRocha, Stellenbosch University*

Desire Lines and Rhizomatic Learning: Speculating Curriculum in Response to Preservice Teachers' Digital Agency. *Delecia Davids, Stellenbosch University*

Their family has capital too: Black female first-generation graduate students' Experiences of parent support. *Le-Anne Lezhaan Goliath, Stellenbosch University*

South African Employer Brand Positioning: A Content Analysis of Graduate Job Adverts. *Nthabeleng Rammile, Stellenbosch University*

Chair: *Joel Samoff, Stanford University*

Discussant: *Joel Samoff, Stanford University*

52.079-2. Unforgetting Family Wisdom: Immigrant Journeys, Engagement, and Educational Futures (Table 2).

Division A - Administration; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Districtwide Family Engagement Strategies and Chronic Absenteeism Among California's Kindergarteners and Multilingual Learners. *Kevin A. Gee, University of California - Davis*

International Mothers in Motion: Navigating and Supporting Their Children's Educational Journeys in the U.S. *Fatemeh Mozaffari, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

Meaningful Changes Matter: Latent Transitions of Parental Involvement and their Effects on Adolescents' Mental Health. *Yiwen Tang, Beijing Normal University; Linyuan Deng, Beijing Normal University; Xiaomei Yu, Panzhihua Experimental School, Sichuan Province, China; xiaohang luo, Chengdu Normal University*

Chair: *Kristin Vogel-Campbell, North Point Educational Service Center*

52.079-3. Pop Pedagogies: Rethinking Education Through Film, Music, and Math (Table 3). Division B - Curriculum Studies; Roundtable Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Probing Democracy: Preservice Teachers Apply Critical Media Literacy to Christopher Nolan's Batman: The Dark Knight. *Robert L Sobel, The University of Texas at Austin; Mathew Baker, Georgia Southern University*

The Trap: Using Hip Hop to Center and Critical Consciousness. *Jonathan Tunstall, Bowdoin College*

Unforgetting Turtle Geometry: Making Geometry Education More Visual, Computational, and Culturally-Relevant. *Sina Rismanchian, University of California - Irvine; Shayan Doroudi, University of California - Irvine*

Chair: *Nathan Alexander, Howard University*

52.079-4. Creative Curriculum & Playful Pedagogies (Table 4).

Division B - Curriculum Studies; Roundtable Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Mapping English Curriculum: Text Set Assemblages and the Linked Text Set Map. *Austin Jerrod Unowitz, University of Connecticut*

Enhancing Creativity and Entrepreneurship in Higher Education: A Systematic Review Based on Self-Determination Theory. *XINTONG LI, The Education University of Hong Kong; Xiaojing Weng, The Education University of Hong Kong*

Toward a Clown(ing) Pedagogue: (Re)thinking Curriculum through a Clown Process Ontology. *Joseph D. Sweet, University of North Carolina - Pembroke; Amalie Strange, Arizona State University*

Why Can't We Play?: A Collaborative Autoethnography of Incorporating Playfulness into Pedagogical Practices. *Shannon Perry, Valdosta State University; Yixuan Wang, Gwinnett County Public Schools*

Chair: *Joseph D. Sweet, University of North Carolina - Pembroke*

52.079-5. Something about the Human through Fascist Rise and Global Fall (Table 5). Division B - Curriculum Studies; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

AI and Normalizing a Nuclear Renaissance? Worthwhile Curriculum and Human Education in the Anthropocene. *Jason Goulah, DePaul University*

Investigating Organizational Collaboration in Curriculum Reform: An Actor-Network Theory Perspective on Boundary Objects. *Chin-Ju Mao, National Taiwan Normal University*

Towards an Anti-Fascist Global Citizenship Education. *Dani Friedrich, Teachers College, Columbia University; Cinthia Wanschelbaum, Universidad de Buenos Aires*

Chair: *Kevin D. Lam, Drake University*

52.079-6. Global lenses in curriculum studies (Table 6). Division B - Curriculum Studies; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Global Citizenship Competencies in Africana Studies: A Quantitative Ethnographic Study. *Tiffany Dupree Osei, University of Pennsylvania*

Heritage as Friction: Teaching Through Tensions of Curriculum, Identity, and Belonging. *Andrea Lira, Universidad de Magallanes*

Neutrality as Curriculum: Unmasking Swiss Mythologies in Global Economic Memory. *Meya Elizabeth Hargett, Pepperdine University*

Pluriversal Examinations of Teachers' Encounters with the

Violent Past in Guatemala. *Charlotte Haynes, Teachers College*

Chair: *Charlotte Haynes, Teachers College*

52.079-7. Adolescent Pathways: Exploring Parental Influence, Neurodiversity, and Purpose in Youth (Table 7). Division E - Counseling and Human Development; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Everyday Heroism Expands Commitment to Hobbies and Leisure Among Adolescents and Young Adults. *Theresa A. Thorkildsen, University of Illinois at Chicago*

When Parents and Teens Disagree: How Matched and Mismatched Perceptions of Parental Involvement Shape Academic Success. *Luyang Guo, University of Macau*

Chair: *April Z. Taylor, California State University - Northridge*

52.079-8. The Evolving Landscape of Improvement: Theorizing for the Future of Improvement in Education (Table 8). SIG-Improvement Science in Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

The Practice of Improvement Research in Education: A Comparative Analysis of Improvement Methodologies in Local Contexts. *Angela Lyle, Wayne State University; Daniel Zelig Marks, Vanderbilt University; Donald J. Peurach, University of Michigan; Jennifer Lin Russell, Vanderbilt University*

Building Axiological Rigor for Centering Justice in Continuous Improvement. *Carlos Sandoval, Clemson University; Rebecca Colina Neri, Stemuli Studios, Inc.; Erica Misako Boas, San Francisco State University*

Improvement Research Penetration in State Education Agencies: Putting Big Data to Work. *Peilin Qiu, University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill; Lora Cohen-Vogel, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Nina Wetoska*

Puzzling Positionalities: A New Role for Researchers in Continuous Improvement. *Christine M. Neumerski, University of Maryland*

Chair: *David H. Eddy-Spicer, University of Virginia*

52.079-9. Critical Perspectives in Educational Leadership (Table 9). SIG-Leadership for Social Justice; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Centering Cultural Awareness and Community: Reimagining Social Emotional Learning for Equity and Inclusion. *Tarisai Lumumba-Umoja, DC Public Schools*

The Cilantro Effect: Reimagining Leadership Through Relational Risk and Transparent Care. *Sarah Elisa Stein, San Francisco State University*

Leading from the Margins: Reimagining Educational Leadership Through Black Feminist and Critical Race Theories. *Charo D. Darwin, Claremont Graduate University*
Sociocultural and Critical Race Perspectives on Arab American Women's Leadership in U.S. K-12 Public Schools. *Suha Hammoudeh, Paterson Public Schools; Heejung An, William Paterson University*

Broadening Leadership Lens: How Diverse Educational Leaders Expand Social and Cultural Capital for Equity-Oriented Change. *Anindya Kundu, Florida International University; Steven Michael Carlo, Monmouth University; Becca Huntting, New York University*

Chair: *Carla Finkelstein, Towson University*

52.079-10. Mentoring in STEM Contexts and Programs (Table 10). SIG-Mentorship and Mentoring Practices; Roundtable Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

A Holistic Approach to Supporting Underrepresented Minority Faculty in STEM. *Onyinyechukwu Onu Onwuka, University of North Carolina - Greensboro; Mercy Ama Blematessa, University of North Carolina - Greensboro; Eunice Oduro, University of North Carolina - Greensboro; Renā A. S. Robinson, Vanderbilt University; Danelle Stevens-Watkins, University of Kentucky; Aileen Reid, University of North Carolina - Greensboro*

Faculty of Color Engaging in Authentic Care in Mentoring in STEM Summer Research Internships. *Courtney L. Luedke, University of Illinois at Chicago; Angelina Lavinia Grace Ortiz, University of Illinois at Chicago*

'Feeling Out of Place': Impostor Phenomenon Among BIPOC and LGBTQ STEM College Students. *Richard Chang, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Diana Beltran, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Shanika Wickramarachchi, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Gloria Wong-Padoongpatt, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Rachael Robnett, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Aelxis Rice, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*

Networked Mentorship and Cultural Integration: Understanding Indigenous Motivation and Persistence in STEM. *K. Kanoho Hosoda, University of Hawaii - Manoa; Rachelle M. Pedersen, Texas Tech University; Kathy DeerInWater, American Indian Science & Engineering Society; Brittany Anderson, AISES*

Chair: *Cecilia D Craig, Independent Researcher*

52.080. AERA Roundtable Session Friday 9:45 am - Gold 1; Roundtable Session

52.080-1. Networks, trust, and belonging for underrepresented students (Table 1). Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Academic Identity Through Embedded Academic Networks: Evidence from Chinese Graduate Students. *Jiaqi He, Nanjing University; yunyi luo, East China Normal University*

Against the Current! Navigating the PHD Tide while Black and Female at a PWI. *Kimberly D. Lloyd, WGYC Inc; Seville Sawyer, Murray State University*

A Seat at the Table: Black Men's Motivations and Experiences in Doctoral Counselor Education. *Demetrius Cofield, The Ohio State University; Brittany N. Glover, San Diego State University; Sara Jean-Philippe, University of Florida*

Beyond Latine Enrollment: Fostering Critical Consciousness and Identity Development at a Hispanic-Serving Institution. *Darlis Pantoja-Benavides, University of Connecticut; Kevin Ferreira van Leer, University of Connecticut; Amber Michelle Gonzalez, California State University - Sacramento; Anytra I Culbreath-Evans, University of Connecticut*

Not on the Menu: Korean American Students' Reflections on Campus Food and Belonging. *Damhee Dee Dee Hong, University of California - Santa Barbara*

52.080-2. Roundtable 2 (Table 2). Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Stories of success in STEM: Composite counter-narratives of non-dominant pathways for minoritized students. *Danielle Vegas Lewis, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Sarah A. Hale, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Megan Holland Iantosca, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Shelley Kimelberg, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

Program Assessment: Career Development Services as Informed by Black Female Undergraduates in Engineering. *Candice A. Kelly, Auburn University*

The Emperor's New Careers: Rhetoric and Reality of Employability. *Laura Dean, University of Sheffield*

"What Was College Made For?": Exploring College Students' Civic Engagement Outcomes by College Major. *Carlton J. Fong, Texas State University; Kristen P. Kremer, Kansas State University*

Chair: *Sze Ling Hung, University of Iowa*

52.080-3. Faculty Issues amid Political Change in Academia (Table 3). Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;

9:45-11:15am

Participants:

How Inclusive R1s Sustain Workplace Belonging for Black and Hispanic Engineering Faculty. *Henry Tran, University of South Carolina; Spencer Platt, University of South Carolina; Kerwin Johnson, University of South Carolina*

Racialized power and whiteness: Leveraging whiteness as a credential to support or resist faculty diversity. *Deborah E. Southern, University of California - Los Angeles; Mitchell J. Chang, University of California - Los Angeles; Gabriel Lé Espiritu, University of California - Los Angeles*

Reframing Leadership: Faculty Perspectives on Non-Academic Presidents at R1 Universities. *Amita Verma, University of South Carolina; Susan C. Bon, Pittsburg State University*

Not Just Boxes to Check: Faculty Agency and the Everyday Politics of DEI in STEM. *Wu Xie, University of Missouri; Candace R. Kubly, University of Missouri*

Relational Work and Racialized Recognition: Emotional Labor Among Men of Color Practitioners at Hispanic Serving Institutions. *Adrian H. Huerta, University of Southern California; Jose Bermejo, University of Southern California; Nevan Bell, University of California - Santa Barbara*

Chair: *Jaden Alexandra Mikoulinskii, University of Georgia*

52.080-4. Supporting and Retaining Today's Faculty (Table 4).

Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Faculty Participation in Community-Engaged Scholarship and Artistry: A Mixed Methods Study. *Alexios Rosario-Moore, Northern Illinois University; Emelia Essumanba-Josiah, Northern Illinois University; Haider Thahab, Northern Illinois University*

From Commitment to Constraint: Community College Faculty Discourse Amid Growing Precarity and Institutional Shifts. *Ashley N. Gaskew, Baruch College - CUNY; Shelby Rogers, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Motivation to Stay: Retaining Global Talent in Chinese Universities. *Kexin Long, Shanghai Jiao Tong University; Xiaoqiao Zhang, Shanghai Jiao Tong University; Haroon Hakimi, Shanghai Jiao Tong University*

Chair: *Alexios Rosario-Moore, Northern Illinois University*

52.080-5. Belonging from the Beginning: Intentional Policy, Practices, and Inquiry in Early Childhood Education (Table 5).

Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education;
Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Fostering Inquiry in Early Childhood: Analyzing Preservice Teachers' Use of Primary Sources to Foster Wonder. *Daria Smirnova, University of South Florida; Anthony Woode-*

Eshun, University of South Florida; Ilene R. Berson, University of South Florida; Michael J. Berson, University of South Florida

Latent Profiles of Intentional Language Teaching Among Chinese Kindergarten Teachers. *Yongjia Yu, University of Hong Kong; Carrie Lau, University of Hong Kong; Zhiyi Han, Chinese University of Hong Kong*

The Relationship Between Rural Areas' Early Childhood Education Teachers' Autonomy, Belonging, Job Satisfaction, and Burnout. *Maryam Sadat Sharifian, James Madison University*

Early Childhood Educators' Experiences Cultivating Academics Belonging and Criticality in Early Childhood Literacy Classrooms. *Amber Lawson, Bowling Green State University; Ashelin R. Currie, Oakland Schools; Rylee Smith, Bowling Green State University*

From Policy to Playground: Reimagining Play-Based Learning Through Collaborative Analysis. *Karen Walker, East Texas A&M University; Rodrick Whitley, East Texas A&M University*

Chair: *Amber Lawson, Bowling Green State University*

52.080-6. Coaching, Mentoring, and Professional Learning: Collective Support in Teacher Preparation (Table 6).

Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

How Do Student Teachers Perceive Their Mentor Teachers' Interventions During Teaching? *Nicole Bosse, Friedrich-Schiller-Universität Jena; Alexander Groeschner, Friedrich-Schiller-Universität Jena*

"Just Keep Building Your Knowledge Base": Mentor Teachers' Evaluations of Secondary Pre-Service Teachers. *Edgar Diaz, Utah State University; Anda Grace Pearson, Utah State University*

Reimagining the Residency Site Curriculum: Designing for Critical Mentorship in Support of Inclusive Teaching. *Sarah L. Schlessinger, New York University; Karoline Trepper, New York University*

Strengthening the Teacher Residency Design: Lessons Learned from Resident and Mentor Teachers. *Jennifer Alayne Tygret, Illinois College; Sylvia L. Mendez, University of Kentucky; Ji Hyun Oh, University of Colorado - Colorado Springs*

Building Alignment Between Student Teaching Placements and Teacher Preparation Programs Through In-the-Moment Coaching Triads. *Kathy Liu Sun, Santa Clara University; Kathleen Jablon Stoehr, Santa Clara University*

Chair: *Jennifer Alayne Tygret, Illinois College*

52.080-7. Potpourri of In-Service Educator Development (Table 7).

Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education;
Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

An Overview of Reviews of Research on Teacher

Collaboration: Typologies and Future Directions. *Huang Wu, University of Missouri - Kansas City; Xueli Shi, East China Normal University*

Arts Integration Teacher Professional Development: Teacher and Student Agency. *Kendall LaParo, Research for Action; Julia Camille Ransom, Research for Action; Sean Vannata, Research for Action*

Centering Student Voice: Insights into Self-Regulated Learning from Classroom Survey Data. *Tara Miyoko Kintz, Michigan Assessment Consortium; John Lane, Michigan Assessment Consortium; Hilary Johannes, Chandler Unified School District; Sean Carmody, Retired - High School*

Motivated to Innovate: The Role of Teachers' Collaboration and Expectancy-Value Beliefs in Cognitive Activation Practices. *Juyoung Lee, Busan Metropolitan City Office of Education; Iksang Yoon, Pusan National University*

Predicting Movement Integration in the Classroom by Teacher Characteristic Profiles. *Tjari Malou Klimpki, Universität Hamburg; Tim Heemsoth, Europa-Universität Flensburg*

Chair: *Shuo Zhao, University of Hawaii - Hilo*

52.080-8. Reimagining HBCU Pedagogies and Policies for Black Futures (Table 8). SIG-Research Focus on Black Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

A Different World: Reclaiming Student Engagement Theory and Practice at HBCUs. *Janeula M. Burt, Bowie State University*

Comments, Conflict, and Celebration: Examining Social Media Responses to HBCU Pride Month Posts on Facebook. *Dalvin Trevon Dunn, Texas A&M University; Darius Adams, Michigan State University; Lamont Davis, University of Texas at Austin; Jarrel T. Johnson, University of Utah*

Identifying Paternalistic Policies: A Critical Examination of Student Handbooks at a Historically Black University. *Chelsia Ivey Douglas, University of Delaware*

Unapologetically Black and Unforgettably Bold: Reclaiming Resistance and Reimagining Political Futures at HBCUs. *Amanda Wilkerson, University of Central Florida; Shalander L. Samuels, Kean University*

Chair: *Wawanza Kalonji Rand, Teachers College, Columbia University*

52.081. AERA Roundtable Session Friday 9:45 am - Gold 2;
Roundtable Session

52.081-1. Language, Policy, and Possibility: Reimagining

Educational Futures for Multilingual Learners (Table 1).

Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Appropriate for Whom? Rethinking Equity in New Jersey's Bilingual Education Code. *Claudia M. Castillo-Lavergne, Rutgers University - Newark; Swati Dontamsetti, Rutgers University; Vandeen Campbell, Rutgers University - Newark; Isabella Rojas, Rutgers University - Newark*

Evaluating the Effects of Reclassification from the Four-Hour English Language Development Block in Arizona: A Regression Discontinuity Approach. *Lindsey A. Brown, Arizona State University*

Hundreds of Plans for California's Million English Learners: A Statewide Review of District EL Master Plans. *Isabel Clay-Frum, University of Southern California; Margaret Dawson-Amoah, University of Southern California; Junmin Byon, University of Southern California*

Implementing English Language Development Standards and Transformative Practices in a Rural School District—A Case Study Approach. *Hannah Park, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Timothy J. Boals, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Chair: *Andrea Louise Ochoa, Brown University*

52.081-2. Centering Marginalized Narratives in Music Education (Table 2). SIG-Music Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

A Narrative Case Study on The Standard Bearer-Educator Perspective of Teaching African American Spirituals. *Michelle Zazaax Gibson, California State University - Long Beach*

Baton, Body, and Belonging: Narratives of First-Generation Asian American Women on the "Glass Podium". *Katy Jeong Cheng Ho Weatherly, University of Macau*

"This Is a Win Not Just for Me": A Multiple-Case Study of First-Generation Latiné Musicians. *Nabile Galvan, Colorado State University*

This Woman's Worth: A Narrative Study on the Impact of Childhood Sexual Abuse on the Voices of Black women and Black girls. *Ashira Mothersil, Teacher's College, Columbia University*

Chair: *Drew Xavier Coles, Teachers College, Columbia University*

52.081-3. Memory, History, and Reclaiming Narratives in Education (Table 3). SIG-Narrative Research; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Constructing a Chicana Scholar Identity Through Autoethnographic Testimonio and Anzaldúan Frameworks. *Genevie C. Rodríguez-Quiñones, University of Texas at San Antonio*

From Roots to Branches: Mapping Educational Journeys Through Generations. *Anastasia Lavrenyuk, University of Maryland*

Looking Back to Move Forward: Insights from Utilizing Indigenous Research Methods. *Iesha Jackson, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Catharine Lory, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Camisha Fagan, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Vanessa Nunez, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*

“Unforgetting” the Calling: Reclaiming Memory and Reimagining Futures in Education for Educational Research. *Gia Roberts, Broward County Public Schools*

Chair: *Sharon H. Ulanoff, California State University - Los Angeles*

52.081-4. Building the Bridge: Developing Tailored Induction Models for Diverse Early-Career Educators (Table 4).

SIG-Research on Teacher Induction; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Communities of Practice as Comprehensive Induction for Early Career Early Childhood Educators. *Melissa Siller, University of the Incarnate Word*

Beyond Traditional Mentoring: The Differential Effects of Dual-role Participation on Early-career Teachers' Efficacy and Teaching Practices. *Moonyoung Eom, Seoul National University*

Supporting Secondary Novice STEM Teachers through a Mentor-Mentee Yearlong Induction Program. *Karen E. McIntush, University of Houston; Karla Adelina Garza, University of Houston; Paige K. Evans, University of Houston*

Chair: *Meixi *, University of Minnesota*

Discussant: *Maria A. Flores, University of Minho*

52.081-5. Modern Emerging Issues in Rural Education (Table 5).

SIG-Rural Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

A Critical Content Analysis of Rural Education Research Pre- and Post-2016. *Karen Eppley, Pennsylvania State University; Mara C. Tieken, Bates College; Maya Eppley, Aston Carter*

Opening Rural Pathways to Computational Thinking and AI: Exploring Motivation Among Economically Disadvantaged Primary Students. *Chun-Ping Wu, National University of Tainan; Fu-Yun Yu, National Cheng Kung University*

Reimagining Civic Trust in Rural Higher Education:

Institutional Rural Consciousness and Stewardship of Political Place. *Katie L. Kleinhesselink, University of Colorado - Boulder*

The Impact of COVID and Learning Support Services on Students' Academic Outcomes and Postsecondary Enrollment. *Jui-Teng Li, Appalachian State University; Catherine Parks, Appalachian State University; Corinne Smith, Appalachian State University; James Beeler, Appalachian State University; Kathryn Watson, Appalachian State University; Hayden Laws, Appalachian State University; Shawn McNulty, Appalachian State University*

We Knew... We Should Have Known. Troubled Stories of Rural College Closure. *Josh Montgomery, Northland College; Dani O'Brien, Northland College*

Chair: *Wendy Pfrenger, University of Mississippi*

52.081-6. Reimagining Rural Schools Worldwide: Policy, Community Engagement, and Student Development (Table 6).

SIG-Rural Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Cultivating Positive Emotions through Choral Instruction: An Empirical Study in Rural Chinese Primary School. *Yinyi Luo, East China Normal University*

Education and spatial reproduction: How does education perpetuate rural-urban spatial inequality in China? *Yuan Teng, Central China Normal University*

Innovative development research of rural small schools: A Fujian elementary school study. *Jiani Wu, Fujian Normal University; Vincy Ruan, Fujian Normal University; Qiaowa Zeng, Fujian Normal University*

Intercultural Bilingual Border Schools: A Case Study of Misiones, Argentina-Brasil. *Alfredo Andres Villalba, Ministry of Education in Misiones and Hertford County; Charles L. Lowery, Virginia Tech*

Understanding Two Targeted Teacher Education Policies in China: A Person-Centered Study of Teaching Intention. *Yuwei Luo, Beijing Normal University; Naiyi Wang, Beijing Normal University*

Chair: *Yilang Zhao, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

52.081-7. Early Learning and Equitable Access: Language, Practice, and Equity (Table 7).

SIG-Special and Inclusive Education Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

How Home Language(s) Shape Early Intervention Exit: Unpacking Equitable Access. *Maiko Hata, University of Oregon*

Teacher Talk During Interactive Read-Aloud with Preschoolers with Autism: A Descriptive Analysis. *Xiaoning Wang, Denison University; Phuong Ta, University of Alabama -*

Birmingham

Rethinking What You Think You Know: Early Childhood Special Educators' Critical Reflection on Their Practice. *Yoon-Joo Lee, Brooklyn College - CUNY; Susan L. Recchia, Teachers College, Columbia University*

From Self-Efficacy to Systems Change: Understanding the Challenges Facing Inclusive Preschool Education Initiatives. *Kaitlin K. Moran, Saint Joseph's University; Mary E. Sheppard, Saint Joseph's University; Cindy Collado, California State University - Sacramento; Andrea Golloher, San José State University*

Chair: *Mbuh G Payne, Rowan University*

52.081-8. Equity, Advocacy, and Inclusive Futures: Perspectives on Special Education Practices (Table 8).

SIG-Special and Inclusive Education Research; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Intersectional-Coalition-Building through Cross-Generational Conversations for the Future of IDEA: A Duo-Autoethnographic Study. *Barbara L. Pazez, University of North Texas; David I. Hernandez-Saca, University of Northern Iowa*

Becoming Change Agents: Stories of Pre-Service Special Educators of Color. *Jemma Kim, California State University - San Bernardino; Sherri Franklin-Guy, California State University - San Bernardino; Young Suk Hwang, California State University - San Bernardino*

Assemblages of Marginality: Exploring the Geographic and Structural Displacement of Homeless Students with Disabilities. *Yehyang Lee, Syracuse University; Dian Mawene, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Dosun Ko, Santa Clara University*

Teachers' Emotional Landscapes & Attitudinal Frameworks: A Cross-Cultural Study of SEND Pedagogical Practices. *Litong QI, Hong Kong Shue Yan University; Luis Miguel Dos Santos, Hong Kong Shue Yan University, Hong Kong; Hongyan Wang, Binghamton University - SUNY; Ying Li, Binghamton University - SUNY*

Chair: *Chelsea Tracy-Bronson, Stockton University*

52.081-9. Exploring Disability Identity and Student Agency (Table 9). SIG-Special and Inclusive Education Research; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Figuring Inclusion: School-Based Discourses and the Construction of Disability and Agency. *Katie Baulier, Endicott College*

"I Push Myself": How a (Dis)abled Black Girl Navigated Mathematics Identity Socialization in Middle School.

Camille Griffin, Saint Xavier University

Remembering "Christina" Black Students with Learning Disabilities: A New Vision for Teaching Writing. *Latesha Watson, Temple University; Ayodele Patience Aborishade, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Lola Aneke, University of North Texas*

Centering Students with Intellectual Disability in IPSE Research: A Secondary Analysis. *Katie E. Ducett, SUNY - College at Cortland; Beth Myers, Syracuse University; Sara Jo Soldovieri, The IDEAL School; Nikkia D. Borowski, Syracuse University; Cam Michael Powell, Syracuse University; Rebekah Wallis, Syracuse University; Ethan W Jackson, Syracuse University*

From Plans to Possibility: Centering the Lived Futures of Young Women with Disabilities. *Kara Hirano, Search Institute; Lauren Lindstrom, University of California - Davis*
Chair: *Elizabeth Harkins, William Paterson University*

52.082. AERA Roundtable Session Friday 9:45 am - Gold 3; Roundtable Session

52.082-1. Accessing Historical Content: Analyzing Materials for Learning History (Table 1). SIG-Teaching History; Roundtable Session

Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

A Comparative Analysis of U.S. and Chinese History Textbooks' Narratives on 20th Century U.S. Imperialism. *Chenyu Li, Indiana University - South Bend; Kason Kendall, Utah State University*

Beyond Play: Historical Games as Platform for Immersive Learning. *Farzan Baradaran Rahimi, Grant MacEwan University*

Is Historical Inquiry Critical?: A Quantitative Content Analysis of US History Lessons. *Eric Claravall, California State University - Sacramento; Elizabeth Isidro, Western Michigan University*

Justifying Imperialism and Silencing the Marginalized in History Education. *Anna Yonas, University of Kansas; Stephen J. Jackson, University of Kansas*

52.082-2. Material-Discursive Pedagogies and Curriculum (Table 2). SIG-Critical Posthuman and Postfoundational Studies in Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Materialities of Exclusions and (re)Participation: A Case study of Korean Language Arts Classrooms. *Sungwon Cho, Seoul National University; Kyunghye So, Seoul National University; Jiyoung Kim, Seoul National University; Taegeun Yum, Seoul National University; Soohan Lee, Seoul National University*

(Re)Searching Mathematical Thinking-Diagramming

Entanglement in a Primary School in China: A Postfoundational and Posthuman Revisit. *Weili Zhao, Hangzhou Normal University*

Strings Across Intercultural Borders: Disrupting Curriculum through the lens of New Materialism. *Caroline Pearsall, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Mission (Im)possible: A Critical Genealogy of the Mission Statement Genre and Its Limits. *Courtney Martinez, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Chair: *Laura M. Jewett, University of Texas - Rio Grande Valley*

52.082-3. Afrofuturism, Sankofa, and the Radical Imagination in Black Educational Thought (Table 3). SIG-Research Focus on Black Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Co-Creating the Sankofa Framework: Humanizing Research Through Reflexivity and Critical Consciousness. *Ashley N. Gibson, Baylor University*

"For Us, By Us": Centering Black Language, Culture, and Community in Scholarly Publishing. *Mia Harris, Stanford University; Ramon Stephens, Stanford University*

Pursuing Educational Equity with Afrofuturism and Futures Scenario Planning. *Darnel Degand, University of California - Davis; Sosanya M. Jones, Howard University*

52.082-4. Intersections of STEM and Females (Table 4). SIG-Research on Women and Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

"I don't identify with STEM much anymore": Exploring Decline in Women of Color's STEM Identity. *Jasmyne Yeldell, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Anina Mahmud, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Simone Wilson, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Dionne Cross Francis, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*

STEM Space-Makers: Exploring STEM Disciplinary Agency of Women of Color Graduate Students in a Global Context. *Seonmi Jin, Indiana University*

Uncovering AP STEM Gaps for Girls of Color in Harris County High Schools. *Jesus Campos, Harris County Department of Education*

WoC Persisting in STEM: Story of Strength. *Anina Mahmud, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Dionne Cross Francis, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*

52.082-5. Mobility and Stratification in Postsecondary Education and Beyond (Table 5). SIG-Sociology of Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;

9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Changes in the Effect of the Childhood Socioeconomic Status on U.S. Adults' Cognitive Skills. *Wan Yu, Chung-Ang University*

High Earnings In STEM? It's A Myth For PhD Women In Physical/Chemical Sciences. *Yun Kyung Cho, Northwestern University*

How Do First-generation College Students Achieve Upward Educational Mobility? A Dynamic Mechanism Analysis of Postgraduate Aspiration in China. *Huafeng Zhang, Shanghai Normal University; Fei Guo, Tsinghua University; Tianle Shi, Tsinghua University*

Medical School Craze and STEM Stratification: An Exploratory Study of South Korea's College Major Choice. *Seoyoung Lim, Arizona State University*

Neither High Nor Low: Chinese Middle-Class Families' Strategic Choice of Sino-Foreign Cooperative Universities. *Kai Zhao, Lingnan University; Yuyun Yang, Lingnan University; Jiaxin GUO, Lingnan University*

Chair: *Cassandra Victoria Guzman, Cornell University*

52.082-6. Critical Examination of Race, Ethnicity, Class, and Gender Roundtable: The Digital Age and Its Discontents, Critical Media Literacies (Table 6). SIG-Critical Examination of Race, Ethnicity, Class and Gender in Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

"Feminism is Essential, But...": A Critical Discourse Analysis of ChatGPT Outputs Under Different Prompting Conditions. *Apala Biswas, University of Cincinnati; Mark A. Sulzer, University of Cincinnati; Mazid Ul Hasan, University of Cincinnati*

Critical Media Literacy and Palestine: Educators Analyzing Media Discourse to Humanize Palestinian Voices. *Hanadi Shatar, California State University - Sacramento; Amanda Najib, New York University*

Teenage girls' responses to unsolicited violent and sexually explicit content shared on social media. *Raksha Janak, University of Pretoria; Diloshini Govender, University of the Witwatersrand; Deevia Bhana, University of KwaZulu-Natal; Shaaista Moosa, University of KwaZulu-Natal*

Exploring Agency in Digital Racial Representation: Teacher Racial Literacies and Archaeology of Self. *Robyn Ilten-Gee, Simon Fraser University; Pooja Dharamshi, Simon Fraser University; Jabari Mahiri, University of California - Berkeley*

Chair: *Wenyu Guo, University of South Florida*

52.082-7. Enhancing family-school connections: Student engagement or outcomes (Table 7). SIG-Family, School, Community Partnerships; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- How Does Family Educational Investment Depend on Children's Academic Ability? An Experiment on Information Shocks. *Xinjie Zhang, Vanderbilt University; Yi Wei, Peking University; Yingquan Song, Peking University; Feifan Zhang, The Education University of Hong Kong*
- Evaluating a Family Engagement Intervention to Strengthen Family-School Connections and Student Outcomes. *Danielle R. Harrell, University of Texas - Arlington; Ambra Green, University of Texas - Arlington; Aundraea Brown, University of Texas - Arlington; Juterh Nmah, California State University, Bakersfield; Angela Jeanette Hall, University of Texas - Arlington*
- Students' Perceptions of Homework Feedback Quality: Do Homework Purpose, Effort, and Management Matter? *Ruiping Yuan, Mississippi State University; Jianzhong Xu, Mississippi State University*
- Understanding Families' Beliefs and Experiences During the Transition from Head Start to Kindergarten. *Cristin McDonough, Portland State University; Fiona Weiss, Portland State University; Andrew Mashburn, Portland State University; Karlyn R. Adams-Wiggins, Portland State University*

Chair: *Sandra Barrueco, The Catholic University of America*

52.082-8. Social emotional development in diverse contexts (Table 8). SIG-Family, School, Community Partnerships; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- The Effect of Parental Cohesion on adolescent Aggression: the chain-mediated role of Peer Relationships and Academic Stress. *Jinqian Liao, Southwest University*
- Cultural Capital and Decision-Making: Autism Service Choices Among Immigrant Parents. *Hui Zhang, University of Toledo; Sabiha Sultana, University of California - Santa Barbara*
- Grandparental Involvement, Paternal Residency, and Preschoolers' Behavioral Adjustment: The Family System in Contemporary China. *Xinyi PENG, Lancaster University*
- Family Factors Influencing Social-Emotional Development in Children with Disabilities. *Yaoying Xu, Virginia Commonwealth University; Yuyan Xia, University of Kentucky; Chin-Chih Chen, Virginia Commonwealth University*

Chair: *Jessica McCormick, University of Pittsburgh - Greensburg*

52.083. AERA Roundtable Session Friday 9:45 am - Gold 4;
Roundtable Session

52.083-1. Cognition, Confidence, and Emotion: Unpacking Metacognitive and Motivational Dynamics (Table 1).

Division C - Learning and Instruction; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- Investigating the Dynamic Interplay between Test Anxiety and Monitoring Using Mixture Multivariate Growth Curve Modeling. *Yuyang Cai, Shanghai International Studies University; Qianwen Ge, Shanghai International Studies University*
- The Epistemic Engine: Examining Confidence and Reasoning as Relational Factors in Scientific Thinking. *John Rolfe Robertson, University of Maryland; Melike Hanedar, University of Maryland; Teresa Garcia, University of Maryland; Doug Lombardi, University of Maryland*
- Emotion in Motion: Emotion Regulation Among Undergraduate Engineering Students in Their Most Challenging Courses. *Juhee Kim, Florida State University; Jeannine E. Turner, Florida State University; Joseph Gerretz, Florida State University; Pia Rugel, Florida State University*
- Exploring the Complexity of Metacognitive Knowledge About Learning Strategies Among College Students. *Rachel N. Smith-Peirce, Washington University in St. Louis; Madeleine M. M Sapra, Washington University in St. Louis; Andrew C. Butler, Washington University in St. Louis*
- Seductive Details, Cognitive Load, and Academic Achievements: A Multi-level Meta-analysis and MASEM. *Yijun Wu, East China Normal University; Ruobing Wang, East China Normal University; Chao Cheng, East China Normal University; Zhe Wang, East China Normal University*

Chair: *Lauren Cabrera, University of Michigan - Dearborn*

52.083-2. Mixed Methods Frontiers: Leveraging AI in Multiple and Mixed Methods Research (Table 2). Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- Dating and Relationships under a Bluesky: An Educational Data Science Perspective on Communication on BlueSky. *Martin Rehm, University of Southern Denmark; Elisabeth Munth Andersen, University of Southern Denmark*
- Educational Video Transcript Analysis with LLMs: Improving Entity Recognition and Qualitative Insights. *Wei Wang, University of Tennessee; Cody C. Pritchard, University of Tennessee; Joshua Rosenberg, University of Tennessee*
- Exploring the Impact of Adaptive Gamified Assessments on Learner Performance and Motivation in Blended Learning. *Zhihui Zhang, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Yihan Luo, University of Southern California; Thomas K.F. Chiu, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Scott Aubrey, The Chinese University of Hong Kong*

Human-AI Symbiotic Theory (HAIST): Multi-Framework Assessment and AI-Assisted Validation in Academic Research. *Laura Thomsen Morello, University of Bridgeport; John Chick, University of Bridgeport*

Mixed-Method Analysis of Preservice Teachers' Evaluation of AI-Generated Social Justice Lesson Plans. *Younkyung Hong, Ball State University; Yunsoo Park, Iowa State University; Sydney McCammon, Ball State University*

Chair: *Zhaochen Gu, University of Illinois at Chicago*

52.083-3. Exploring innovative pathways for learning: Reflection, network modeling, iterations, and theoretical analysis (Table 3). SIG-Constructivist Theory, Research, and Practice; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Exploring Community and Peer Learning through Leisure Experience Reflection Activities. *Rayyan Zulfiqar, Texas A&M University; Mahjabin Chowdhury, Texas A&M University; heather eden, Texas A&M University*

Network Analysis Uncovers Five Distinct Learning Experiences in a Graduate Instructional Design Course. *Dori Do, University of Alabama - Birmingham; Jonan Phillip Donaldson, University of Alabama - Birmingham*

Resistance, Reflection, Refinement: Researcher Debriefing Towards In-Situ Iterations in a Computational Summer Camp. *David A. Hopping, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Ashita Bawankule, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Santiago Ospina-Tabares, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Mike Tissenbaum, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Understanding Re-Learning Mathematics from Analyzing Constructivist-Based Cognitive Theories. *Michael N. Johnson, University of Iowa*

Chair: *Jannah Walters Nerren, Stephen F. Austin State University*

52.083-4. Informal Learning Environments as Spaces for Building Mathematical and Computational Thinking Skills (Table 4). SIG-Informal Learning Environment Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Exploring Learning Trajectories in Collaborative Educational Games. *Eda Zhang, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Yunseo Lee, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Matthew Berland, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Math at the Museum: Re-visioning Early Math Learning Through a CHAT Lens. *Mandy Dunphy, Baylor University; Tracey R. Jones, Baylor University; Sandra B. Cooper, Baylor University; Margeaux Smith, Baylor University; Andrea Martinez, Baylor University; Michelle Donner, Baylor University; Krystle Moos, Baylor University*

The Contributions of Parent-Child Everyday Problem-Solving Activities to Preschoolers' Computational Thinking: A Three-Wave Longitudinal Study. *Hao Li, University of Hong Kong; Xiao Zhang, University of Hong Kong*

“Vibing with math”: Girls' attitudes towards math during a place-based apprenticeship. *Zahra Jahani, Utah State University; Lisa Lundgren, Utah State University; Brooke Wilder, The EcoLogik Institute; Lubi Lenaburg, University of California - Santa Barbara; Samantha Wynns, The EcoLogik Institute; Natalie Teboul, Traveling Miss T's Math Maps*

52.083-5. Arts based educational research and dance/movement (Table 5). SIG-Arts-Based Educational Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Dancing Bodies, Racialized Futures: Choreopolitical Curriculum and Human Optimization. *Kandyce A. Amie, DePauw University*

Letting Dance Teach. Esthetic Teaching in a Call for an Esthetic Turn in Education. *Paul Edward Moerman, University of Jyväskylä*

Stepping Into the Scene: Invoking Critically Reflective Practice Through Performance. *Felipe Trevisan Ferreira, University of Tennessee; James Coda, University of Tennessee; Liv H. Detwiler, East Tennessee State University*

52.083-6. Arts based educational research for unfolding provocation(s) (Table 6). SIG-Arts-Based Educational Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Learning with the Senses: Diffractive Arts-Based Research in Rural Kazakhstan. *Dilraba Anayatova, Arizona State University*

Relating and Remembering Otherwise: Teaching Repair in Photographic Studies. *Jillian Lerner, University of British Columbia; Rosa Dene David, University of British Columbia*

“There is a Space Saved for Me”: Agency, Art, and Photovoice with Young Artists in New Jersey. *Taylor Masamitsu; Nicole J. Auffant, Rutgers University - Newark; Lynnette Mawhinney, Rutgers University - Newark; Laura Krystal Porterfield, Rutgers University - Newark; Kendall Lipham, Colton Institute of Research and Training*

Chair: *Azmi Azam, University of Arizona*

Discussant: *William Zhou, The George Washington University*

52.083-7. Considering Motivational Pathways and Beliefs in STEM and Beyond (Table 7). SIG-Motivation in Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;

9:45-11:15am

Participants:

From Olympiad to Career: Motivational Transitions and Differentiation Among Former Chinese Mathematical Olympians. *Yijin Lin, East China Normal University; jinhua chen, East China Normal University; Bin Xiong, East China Normal University*

How Undergraduate Students Think of Success and Field-Specific Ability Beliefs in Their Fields. *Yiqiu Yan, University of Texas at Austin; Loryn Bailey, Texas A&M University; Katherine M. Muenks, University of Texas at Austin*

Testing the Brilliance-Belonging Model in HBCU STEM Contexts: Do Established Pathways Hold in Minority-Serving Institutions? *Afiya C. Fredericks, University of the District of Columbia; Sarah Leckey, University of California - Davis; Patrice Greene, University of the District of Columbia; Kali Trzesniewski, University of California - Davis*

The Dual Development Process of Belongingness and Identity of First-Year Engineering Students. *Su Jiang, University of Houston Downtown; Karen E. Rambo-Hernandez, Texas A&M University*

Chair: *Elise C. Allen, University of Northern Colorado*

52.083-8. Student Engagement in Online Learning Environments (Table 8). SIG-Online Teaching and Learning; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Addressing Learner Disengagement in Online Learning Through Chatbots: A Systematic Literature Review for Educational Equity. *Anastasia Shikanova, The Ohio State University*

Creating a Community of Inquiry in an Online Learning Environment. *Lan Liu, University of Macau; Chuang Wang, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Lijia Lin, University of Macau; Susan Oyarzun, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Heather Ramsey, University of North Carolina - Charlotte*

Sustaining Engagement and Interaction in Distance Learning: A Longitudinal Study. *Nikleia Eteokleous, Frederick University; Raphaela Neophytou, Frederick University; Maria Papagianni, Deloitte Development LLC*

Ten Years and One Pandemic Later: Reassessing the Relationships between Student Engagement and Online Learning. *Amber D. Dumford, University of South Florida - Tampa; Angie L. Miller, Indiana University*

The International Other: International Students' Positioning and Engagement in Online Discussions – A Positioning Theory Perspective. *Hajeen Choi, Bowling Green State University; Vanessa Dennen, Florida State University; Dan He, Florida State University; Omer Arslan, Florida State University*

Chair: *Oksana Komarenko, Ball State University*

52.083-9. Design-Based Innovations for Informal Learning with AI and Digital Technologies (Table 9). SIG-Informal Learning Environment Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Supporting Families to Read and Talk Together with a Library Digital Toolkit Program: Results from a Design-based Research Study. *Heather Toomey Zimmerman, Pennsylvania State University; Elisabeth L. Grinder McLean, Pennsylvania State University; Yanping Xu, Pennsylvania State University; Esther Prins, Pennsylvania State University; Carol Clymer, Pennsylvania State University*

Generative AI with Maker-Based Learning: An Exploratory Study from Family STEM Sessions. *Yong Ju Jung, University of Oklahoma; Jiqun Liu, University of Oklahoma*
Examining the Use and Motivation of Vlog-Assisted Informal Language Learning (VAILL): Questionnaire Development and Validation. *Lanfeng Sun, University of Hong Kong; Chin-Hsi Lin, University of Hong Kong; Wai Ming Cheung, University of Hong Kong*

Centering Joy in AI Learning: Reimagining AI Learning Spaces that Celebrate Black and Brown Girls. *Hawra Rabaan, University of Maryland, College Park; Sheena Erete, University of Maryland*

Division and SIG Posters

52.084. AERA Poster Session Friday 9:45am; Poster Session

52.084-1. STEM Education and Computational Learning Innovations. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 9:45-11:15am

Posters:

1. Authentic Design Project for Preservice Teachers' Computational Thinking Development (Poster 1). *Insook Han, Korea University; Yujung Ko, Incheon National University; Sewon Joo, Florida State University; Seoyeon Choi, Korea University*
2. Building a Generative AI-based Agent to Cultivate Science Curiosity: An Intervention Study (Poster 2). *Zepeng Liu, Shanghai Jiao Tong University; Jin Xie, Shanghai Jiao Tong University; Kui Xie, University of Missouri; Xin Tang, Shanghai Jiao Tong University*
3. Designing Chatbots to Promote Systems Thinking in Environmental Science Education (Poster 3). *Ha Nguyen, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Erick Valdez, Orange County Department of Education; Jennifer Pei, University of California - Irvine; Sara Ludovise, Orange*

County Department of Education; Rossella Santagata,
University of California - Irvine

4. Designing Robotics-Integrated STEM Lessons: Teachers' Challenges and Coping Strategies (Poster 4). , *Doaa Saad Hebrew University of Jerusalem; Janan Saba, Hebrew University of Jerusalem*
5. Digital Tools, Real Classrooms: Investigating Barriers to Mathematics Digital Curriculum Platforms (Poster 5). *Erica Askew, Home; Kiley McKee, WestEd*
6. Examining Self-Efficacy through Movement during VR-based Chemistry Lab Learning: An Optical Flow Analysis Approach (Poster 6). *Megan Wiedbusch, University of Central Florida; Roger Azevedo, University of Central Florida*
7. GenAI Use in Computer Science: Insider Perspectives to Inform Practice (Poster 7). *Farhad Roodi, Purdue University; Nursah Yakut, Purdue University; William R. Watson, Purdue University*
8. Generative AI for Personalized Math: A Framework for Cognitive and Multimodal Adaptation. (Poster 8). *Tangning Pan, University of Pennsylvania*
9. Iterative Design of an Intelligent Tutor for Science Reading Comprehension and Understanding of Visualizations (Poster 9). *Andrea L. Beerwinkle, Sam Houston State University; Jennifer G. Cromley, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Kay Wijekumar, Texas A&M University; Runzhi Chen, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*
10. Mining Spatial Reasoning in Mathematics: Problem-Solving Patterns in a Geometry Digital Game Environment (Poster 10). *Shuchen Liu, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Qingqing Zhou, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Oktaria Kolnel, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Jessica R. Gladstone, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Jina Kang, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*
11. Parental Roles and Actions in an Early Childhood Facebook and Home-Based Family STEM Program (Poster 11). *Valentina Bongiovanni, University of North Florida; Meghan M. Parkinson, University of North Florida; Daniel Dinsmore, University of North Florida*
12. "Read the Book, Learn the Story, Play the Narrative": Augmented Reality Reading Experiences and Comprehension (Poster 12). *Todd S. Cherner, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Kristin L. Papoi, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*
13. Scaling Credentials: Navigating Institutional Barriers to Digital STEM Microcredential Adoption (Poster 13). *Rob Moore, University of Florida; Kent J. Crippen, University of Florida; Sophia Soomin Lee, University of Florida*
14. Understanding Secondary Students' Epistemic Cognition in Designing STEM Artefacts with a Personalized Multi-Agent System (Poster 14). *Lei Gao, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Morris Siu-Yung Jong, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Ching Sing Chai, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Keru Li, The Chinese University of Hong Kong*

52.084-2. Innovating Pedagogy and Technology to Transform Learning Environments.

Division C - Learning and Instruction; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 9:45-11:15am

Posters:

15. Coordinating Minds: Human-AI Teaming and Team Shared Cognition (Poster 15). *Mohammad Amin Samadi, University of California - Irvine; Nia M. Dowell, University of California, Irvine*
16. From Service to STEM: Designing a Service-Learning Environment for Teaching Data Skills to Veterans (Poster 16). *Tomika W. Greer, University of Houston; Prem Durairaj, Data Elevates*
17. "I Learn So Much More with this Format": Gamified Course Design and Student Success (Poster 17). *Shari Fowler, Indiana University - East; Chongning Sun, Indiana University*
18. Mapping Feedback Literacy to Course Contexts and Learning Outcomes: An Explanatory Mixed-Methods Study (Poster 18). *Xin Liu, University of Hong Kong; Lily Min Zeng, University of Hong Kong; Yongyan Li, University of Hong Kong*
19. Promoting Elementary Students' Scientific Inquiry Performance: A Metacognitive Scaffolding-Supported Online Inquiry-Based Learning Approach (Poster 19). *Xin Gao, Beijing Normal University; Xidong Guo, Beijing Normal University; Danhui Zhang, Beijing Normal University*
20. Supporting Speaking Practice in Flipped EFL Classrooms: Effects of a Metaverse-Based Experiential Learning Approach (Poster 20). *Xidong Guo, Beijing Normal University; Xin Gao, Beijing Normal University; Danhui Zhang, Beijing Normal University*
21. Validation of Active Learning Classroom Usage Survey for College Students Introduction (Poster 21). *Yiren Kong, Stony Brook University - SUNY; Young Sik Seo, University at Buffalo - SUNY*
22. Fostering Elementary Students' AI Literacy in a Learning Environment Empowered by Generative AI (Poster 22). *Jiawei Wu, East China Normal University; Lu Cao, Shanghai Jiao Tong University; Min Li, East China Normal University; Shufeng Ma, East China Normal University*

52.084-3. Student Learning in Mathematics Education.

Division C - Learning and Instruction; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 9:45-11:15am

Posters:

23. A Systematic Review of Mathematical and Motivational Factors Related to Algebra Performance (Poster 23). *Elena Silla, University of Delaware; Taylor-Paige Guba, University of Delaware; Andrew Rodrigues, University of*

- Delaware; Ogochukwu Chidinso Anisiobi, University of Delaware; Alex Scanniello, University of Delaware; Christina Areizaga Barbieri, University of Delaware*
24. Impact of a Personalized Math Program on Kindergarteners' Math Learning (Poster 24). *Chun-Wei Kevin Huang, WestEd; I. Yelee Jo, WestEd; Natalie Brezack, WestEd; Linlin Li, WestEd; Mingyu Feng, WestEd; Hee Jin Bang, Age of Learning*
 25. Rethinking Calculus for Computer Science: A mapping Analysis of Topic Relevance (Poster 25). *Lei Liu, Educational Testing Service; Field Watts, Educational Testing Service; Erin Barno, ETS; Titus Teodorescu, Educational Testing Service; Ou Lydia Liu, Educational Testing Service*
 26. Stop and Think: Exploring Middle School Students' Cognitive Reflection and Mature Number Sense (Poster 26). *Patrick Kirkland, University of Notre Dame; Chineme Otuonye, University of Notre Dame; Nicole Campbell, St. Francis de Sales School*
 27. Supporting Student Thinking Through Writing: Teacher Insights from a Mathematics Intervention (Poster 27). *Leonardo Martinez, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Gabriela Zuniga, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Erin M. Smith, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*
 28. Visual Cues Offer a New Vision for Middle School Mathematics Education, Literally (Poster 28). *Avery H. Closser, University of Florida; Jeffrey Bye, California State University - Dominguez Hills; Puyuan Zhang, Worcester Polytechnic Institute; Maegan Colbert, Virginia Tech; Shuqi Yu, Virginia Tech; Ji-Eun Lee, Worcester Polytechnic Institute; Caroline B. Hornburg, Virginia Tech; Erin R Ottmar, Worcester Polytechnic Institute; Puyuan Zhang, Worcester Polytechnic Institute*
 29. Embodied Statistical Reasoning: Using the Body to Make Sense of Statistical Concepts (Poster 29). *Tiffany Reyes-Denis, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Sourabh Garg, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Logan Hillary Lauren, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Junior Bennett, Purdue University; Shereen Oca Beilstein, University of Illinois System; Jason W Morphew, Purdue University; Michelle Perry, University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign; Robb Lindgren, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Karle Flanagan, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*
 30. I Hear What You are Thinking: Elementary Students' Perceptions of Teacher-led Mathematical Think-alouds (Poster 30). *Cathy Marks Krpan, University of Toronto - OISE; Gurpreet Sahmbi, University of Toronto - OISE*
 31. Understanding Cognitive Attributes and Hierarchies of Exponential and Logarithmic Functions: A Hierarchical CDM Framework (Poster 31). *Yufeng Guo, Beijing Normal University; Xuan Shi, The High School Affiliated To Beijing Normal University; Xue-Lan QIU, Australian Catholic University*
 32. Students' Sense of Belonging in Mathematics at a Majority Hispanic High School (Poster 32). *Marie Stevenson; Dalton Marsh, California State University - San Bernardino*
 33. Understanding U.S. Rural Students' Mathematics Performance: A Transfer Learning Approach on PISA 2022 (Poster 33). *Li Zhu, University of Iowa; Hyesun You, University of Iowa; Zhenhan Fang, University of Iowa; Dae S. Hong, University of Iowa*
 34. Influence of Extracurricular Resources on Mathematics Achievement: PISA 2022 Study (Poster 34). *Tukhbita Afroz Nawmi, University at Buffalo - SUNY; HuiHsuan (Shana) Liu, University at Buffalo; Haochu Tian, University at Buffalo - SUNY*
- 52.084-4. Counseling Poster Session A. Division E - Counseling and Human Development; Poster Session**
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 9:45-11:15am
- Posters:
35. Academic Stress and Academic Self-efficacy in Chinese Middle Schoolers: Academic Resilience as Mediator (Poster 35). *Jiaying Huo, Xi'an International University*
 36. Adolescents' Reflections on Their Happiness Malleability Beliefs Following a Positive Psychology Intervention (Poster 36). *Aileen Kangavary, University of South Florida; Sarah Kiefer, University of South Florida; Sarah A. Fefer, University of Massachusetts - Amherst; Shannon M. Suldo, University of South Florida; John M. Ferron, University of South Florida*
 37. Career Needs of Graduate Students in Counselor Education Programs (Poster 37). *Na Mi Bang, Indiana University Indianapolis; Janice A. Byrd, Pennsylvania State University; Valerie Couture, University of Central Arkansas*
 38. Career Reasoning of Children in an International School in China (Poster 38). *Zhouyan Bu, Boston University; Kimberly A.S. Howard, Boston University; Zijin Li, Boston University; Pei Wang, Boston University*
 39. Constructing School Counseling: A Comparative NLP and Discourse Analysis of Three National Frameworks (Poster 39). *Chloe Lancaster, University of South Florida; Sarah Putnam, University of South Florida*
 40. Cultivating hope for STEM college students of color through group counseling in sustainability internships (Poster 40). *Michael D. Hannon, Montclair State University; Anjali Badrinath, Montclair State University; Marcus Taylor Jasmin, Montclair State University; Wanqi Yang, Montclair State University; Kayla Cintron, Montclair State University*
 41. Cultural Self-Disclosure Among BIPOC Supervisors in Cross-Racial Supervision (Poster 41). *Sangmin Park, California State University - Sacramento*
 42. Explorations in Uncertainty: A Developmental Perspective of How Psychotherapists Navigate the Unknown (Poster 42). *Chaparrelle Mogavero-Cline*
 43. From Awareness to Action: High School Counselors Navigating Stereotype Threat in STEM (Poster 43). *Junzhao*

Wang, Arizona State University; Lydia Ross, Arizona State University; Medha Dalal, Arizona State University; Yijia Chen, University of Arizona

44. Imagining Liberatory College Futures: A Culturally Responsive Counseling Intervention (Poster 44). *Christine Jean Yeh, University of San Francisco; Sabita Shrestha, University of San Francisco; Brenda Diaz Ortega, University of San Francisco; Kimberly Hong, University of San Francisco; Shreya Rao, University of San Francisco*
45. Profiles of Distress and Achievement: Latent Class Analysis of Mental Health, Grades, Predicting Postsecondary Plans (Poster 45). *Julio Caesar, Bloomington Public Schools; Carlos Chavez, University of Minnesota; Stacy R. Karl, Minnesota State Colleges and Universities; Michael C. Rodriguez, University of Minnesota*
46. Quantitative Study of Counselors as Social Capital Agents for Undocumented/Citizen Students from Mixed-Status Families (Poster 46). *Jenifer L. Kelson, Claremont Graduate University*
47. Understanding College Access in Immigrant-Origin, Emergent Bilingual Learners: Implications for School and College Counselors (Poster 47). *Elizabeth Vera, Loyola University Chicago; Chelsea Yanuaria, Loyola University Chicago; Clare Furtado, Loyola University Chicago*
48. Understanding Family Support in Career Development: Perspectives Across Generations (Poster 48). *Rachel Cinamon Gali, Tel-Aviv University; Sapir Karov, Tel Aviv University; Nitzan Haiman, Tel Aviv University*
49. What makes them suicidal?: College students' Stress coping method as predictors of suicidal ideation (Poster 49). *Katie K. Koo, University of Georgia; Sohee Kim, University of South Alabama*

52.084-5. Teaching Civic Agency through Co-Creation: A Case of Participatory Curriculum Design. SIG-Action Research; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 9:45-11:15am

Poster:

50. Teaching Civic Agency through Co-Creation: A Case of Participatory Curriculum Design (Poster 50). *Toyosi Stephen Adedara, Baylor University*

52.084-6. Catholic Education Pedagogies: Historical Foundations and Whole-Person Formation. SIG-Catholic Education; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 9:45-11:15am

Posters:

51. Describing Postcolonial Philippine Catholic Higher Education: A Hermeneutic Inquiry into Philippine Augustinian Recollect Teacher Education (Poster 51). *Ionell Jay R. Terogo, The Ohio State University*
52. Dancing with Purpose: Catholic Leaders' and Dance

Educators' Perspectives on Nurturing the Whole Child (Poster 52). *Deoksoon Kim, Boston College; Katrina Borowiec, Boston College; Susan Martinelli Shea, Boston College*

52.084-7. Design and Implementation of Reduced Longitudinal Experiments - Longitudinal Studies Poster Session. SIG-Longitudinal Studies; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 9:45-11:15am

Poster:

53. Design and Implementation of Reduced Longitudinal Experiments (Poster 53). *Le Grande Dolino, Indiana University; Justin Philip Tuazon, University of the Philippines; Leslie Rutkowski, Indiana University*

52.085. e-Lightning Ed-Talk Session 11 - Stage 1. AERA e-Lightning Ed-Talks; AERA Ed Talk
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Exhibit Hall A - Stage 1; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- Teaching Civic Agency through Co-Creation: A Case of Participatory Curriculum Design (Stage 1, 9:50 AM). *Toyosi Stephen Adedara, Baylor University*
- Digital Tools, Real Classrooms: Investigating Barriers to Mathematics Digital Curriculum Platforms (Stage 1, 9:59 AM). *Erica Askew, Home; Kiley McKee, WestEd*
- Examining Self-Efficacy through Movement during VR-based Chemistry Lab Learning: An Optical Flow Analysis Approach (Stage 1, 10:08 AM). *Megan Wiedbusch, University of Central Florida; Roger Azevedo, University of Central Florida*
- GenAI Use in Computer Science: Insider Perspectives to Inform Practice (Stage 1, 10:17 AM). *Farhad Roodi, Purdue University; Nursah Yakut, Purdue University; William R. Watson, Purdue University*
- Iterative Design of an Intelligent Tutor for Science Reading Comprehension and Understanding of Visualizations (Stage 1, 10:26 AM). *Andrea L. Beerwinkle, Sam Houston State University; Jennifer G. Cromley, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Kay Wijekumar, Texas A&M University; Runzhi Chen, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*
- Mining Spatial Reasoning in Mathematics: Problem-Solving Patterns in a Geometry Digital Game Environment (Stage 1, 10:35 AM). *Shuchen Liu, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Qingqing Zhou, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Oktaria Kolnel, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Jessica R. Gladstone, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Jina Kang, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*
- Parental Roles and Actions in an Early Childhood Facebook and Home-Based Family STEM Program (Stage 1, 10:44 AM). *Valentina Bongiovanni, University of North Florida;*

Meghan M. Parkinson, University of North Florida; Daniel Dinsmore, University of North Florida

Coordinating Minds: Human-AI Teaming and Team Shared Cognition (Stage 1, 10:53 AM). *Mohammad Amin Samadi, University of California - Irvine; Nia M. Dowell, University of California, Irvine*

Fostering Elementary Students' AI Literacy in a Learning Environment Empowered by Generative AI (Stage 1, 11:02 AM). *Jiawei Wu, East China Normal University; Lu Cao, Shanghai Jiao Tong University; Min Li, East China Normal University; Shufeng Ma, East China Normal University*

Chair: *Mark Warschauer, University of California - Irvine*

52.086. e-Lightning Ed-Talk Session 11 - Stage 2. AERA e-Lightning Ed-Talks; AERA Ed Talk
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Exhibit Hall A - Stage 2; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Influence of Extracurricular Resources on Mathematics Achievement: PISA 2022 Study (Stage 2, 9:50 AM). *Tukhbita Afroz Nawmi, University at Buffalo - SUNY; HuiHsuan (Shana) Liu, University at Buffalo; Haochu Tian, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

Embodied Statistical Reasoning: Using the Body to Make Sense of Statistical Concepts (Stage 2, 9:59 AM). *Tiffany Reyes-Denis, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Sourabh Garg, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Logan Hillary Lauren, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Junior Bennett, Purdue University; Shereen Oca Beilstein, University of Illinois System; Jason W Morphew, Purdue University; Michelle Perry, University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign; Robb Lindgren, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Karle Flanagan, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

From Awareness to Action: High School Counselors Navigating Stereotype Threat in STEM (Stage 2, 10:08 AM). *Junzhao Wang, Arizona State University; Lydia Ross, Arizona State University; Medha Dalal, Arizona State University; Yijia Chen, University of Arizona*

Cultivating hope for STEM college students of color through group counseling in sustainability internships (Stage 2, 10:17 AM). *Michael D. Hannon, Montclair State University; Anjali Badrinath, Montclair State University; Marcus Taylor Jasmin, Montclair State University; Wanqi Yang, Montclair State University; Kayla Cintron, Montclair State University*

Constructing School Counseling: A Comparative NLP and Discourse Analysis of Three National Frameworks (Stage 2, 10:26 AM). *Chloe Lancaster, University of South Florida; Sarah Putnam, University of South Florida*

Career Reasoning of Children in an International School in China (Stage 2, 10:35 AM). *Zhouyan Bu, Boston University; Kimberly A.S. Howard, Boston University; Zijin Li, Boston University; Pei Wang, Boston University*

Dancing with Purpose: Catholic Leaders' and Dance Educators'

Perspectives on Nurturing the Whole Child (Stage 2, 10:44 AM). *Deoksoon Kim, Boston College; Katrina Borowiec, Boston College; Susan Martinelli Shea, Boston College*

Describing Postcolonial Philippine Catholic Higher Education: A Hermeneutic Inquiry into Philippine Augustinian Recollect Teacher Education (Stage 2, 10:53 AM). *Ionell Jay R. Terogo, The Ohio State University*

Chair: *Thurston Domina, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*

Friday, April 10th, 11:00 am

53.010. Editorial Board Meeting: Teaching Educational Research Methods (TERM) Journal. Affiliated Groups; Board Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Santa Anita A; 11:00am to 3:00pm

Friday, April 10th, 11:45 am

Governance Meetings and Events

54.001. AERA International Relations Committee: Closed Meeting Honoring International Travel Award Recipients. AERA Governance; Governance Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 409AB; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Chair: *Jaekyung Lee, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

54.002. Journal of Educational and Behavioral Statistics: Closed Editorial Board Meeting. AERA Governance; Governance Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 513; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Chair: *John Neikirk, American Educational Research Association*

AERA Related Activities

54.010. AERA Past Presidents Luncheon: Invitation Only. AERA Related Activities; Governance Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 309; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Chairs: *Tabbye M. Chavous, American Educational Research Association; Janelle T. Scott, University of California - Berkeley*

Presidential Sessions

54.011. Grief as Remembrance: An Antidote to Institutional Trauma Across Educational Contexts. AERA Presidential Session; Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 411 (Theatre); 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

If We Aren't Grieving, We Aren't Healing: Grief as a Trauma-Informed Praxis. *Sharim Hannegan-Martinez, University of Michigan*

(Un)deniable Grief & Healing: Historicizing and Futuring Intersectional Grief Literacies Among Black Women Faculty. *Sakeena Everett, University of Connecticut*

Resisting Erasure: Scholasticide during the Gaza Genocide. *Chandni Desai, University of Toronto*

Chair: *Stephanie Cariaga, California State University - Dominguez Hills*

Discussant: *Stephanie Cariaga, California State University - Dominguez Hills*

54.012. Re-remembering the Past and Envisioning the Future to Mobilize the Present: Community Organizers, Activist Scholars, and Funders Connecting Movements for Educational Justice. AERA Presidential Session Cosponsored with SIG-Grassroots Community and Youth Organizing for Educational Justice; Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 406AB; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Spoken Word Artists (opening performance). *Patrice M. Hill, University of California - Davis; Denisha Coco Blossom, University of California - Davis*

Presentations 1 and 2. *Bettina L. Love, Teachers College, Columbia University; David O. Stovall, University of Illinois at Chicago*

Presentations 3, 4 and 5. *Patrice M. Hill, University of California - Davis; Letha Muhammad, Educational Justice Alliance; LuzMarina Serrano, Genders & Sexualities Alliance Network*

Presentations 6 and 7. *Michael Wotorson, Schott Foundation for Public Education; Gisele C. Shorter, Nellie Mae Education Foundation; Precious Waldron-Lopez, Schott Foundation for Public Education*

Chair: *Mark R. Warren, University of Massachusetts - Boston*

Discussant: *Vajra M. Watson, University of Redlands*

54.013. Unforgetting in an Era of Erasure: Resisting Anti-Justice Attacks and Envisioning Futures for Higher Education. AERA Presidential Session; Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 408A; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Law in the Crosshairs: Federalism, Civil Rights, and the Fight for Equity in Higher Education. *Kimberly Jenkins Robinson, University of Virginia School of Law*

Legislating Whiteness: A Critical Discourse Analysis of Policymaker Rhetoric. *Veronica Adele Jones, University of North Texas; Kaleb L. Briscoe, University of Oklahoma*

Interpreting Otherwise: Fugitive Agency and the Reimagining of Racial Justice at UNC. *Uma Mazyck Jayakumar, University of California - Riverside; Rican Vue, University of California - Riverside*

Words That Win or Wither: Framing Racial Equity Amid Ideological Resistance in Higher Education. *Royel M. Johnson, University of Southern California; Terrill O. Taylor, University of Maryland*

Chair: *Walter R. Allen, University of California - Los Angeles*

Discussant: *Julian Vasquez Heilig, Western Michigan University*

AERA Research and Science Policy Sessions

54.014. A Fireside Chat with the Books Editorial Board: Charting Future Directions for the Field. AERA Science and Policy Sessions; Invited Speaker Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 511AB; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Chairs: *Bianca Jontae Baldrige, Harvard University; Vichet Chhuon, University of Minnesota*

Participants: *Travis J. Bristol, University of California - Berkeley; Conra D. Gist, University of Houston; Peter A. Youngs, University of Virginia; Marcia L. Rock, University of North Carolina - Greensboro; Lisa Dieker, University of Kansas*

54.015. From Evidence to Headlines: Engaging Journalists in Challenging Times. AERA Science and Policy Sessions; Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 501B; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Moderator: *Tony Pals, American Educational Research Association*

Panelists: *Jill Barshay, The Hechinger Report; Jaweed Kaleem, Los Angeles Times; Sequoia Carrillo, National Public Radio*

AERA Sessions

54.016. 2025 Distinguished Public Service Award Lecture: Evolving Research for Impact – People, Purposes, and Periods in Time Reflections on Public Service for STEM and Beyond. AERA Sessions Cosponsored with AERA Science and Policy Sessions; Invited Speaker Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 408B; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Chair: *Elizabeth H. DeBray, University of Georgia*

Presenter: *Joan E. Ferrini-Mundy, University of Maine*

Committee Sessions

54.017. Division I Fireside Chat: Constructing a Constellation of Education in the Professions: Insights from Fields.

Graduate Student Council Cosponsored with Division I - Education in the Professions; Invited Speaker Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 402A;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Chair: *Kyoungjin Jang-Tucci, University of Wisconsin - Madison*
Panelists: *Linette P. Ross, National Board of Medical Examiners;*
Kimberly A. White-Smith, University of San Diego;
Junghwan Kim, Texas A&M University; Sarah Rodriguez,
Virginia Tech; Jeremy Wright-Kim, University of Michigan

Division Sessions

54.018. Disrupting Hierarchies, Co-Designing Futures: Community-Centered Visions for Education Research and Praxis. Division A - Administration; Paper Session Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Los Cerritos; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Building Civic Learning Infrastructure through School-Community Networks in Divided Urban Contexts. *Gareth Robinson, Queen's University - Belfast; Gavin Duffy, Queen's University - Belfast; Amy O'Riordan, Queen's University - Belfast*

Structured Subversion: Transforming Systems with Measures That Matter to Youth, Families, and Communities. *Rosa L. Rivera-McCutchen, Hunter College - CUNY; Ann M. Ishimaru, University of Washington; Adrienne C. Goss, Clark Atlanta University*

Race and Power Dynamics in "Equity-centered RPPs": Replicating or disrupting power differentials. *Tia R. Williams, Vanderbilt University; Richard O. Welsh, Vanderbilt University; Zoe Lehmann, Washington University in St. Louis*

Successful Principals' Practices Malleable to Contexts: A Meta-Synthesis of 20 Years of International Case Studies. *Junqi Lin, University of Alabama; Jingping Sun, University of Alabama; Michael A. Lawson, University of Alabama; Bob L. Johnson, University of Alabama*

Chair: *Amanda U. Potterton, University of Kentucky*
Discussant: *Katrina Struloeff, University of Pennsylvania*

54.019. Student Excellence in Uncertain Times: Building Ethical Administrative Capacity amid Crisis in K-12 Schools. Division A - Administration; Paper Session Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, La Cienega; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

A Multiple Case Study of Persistent and Emergent Positive Outlier Schools: How They Build Innovation Capacity Through Past-Informed Future Making. *Kristen C. Wilcox, University at Albany - SUNY; Aaron Leo, University at Albany - SUNY; Jessie Tobin, University at Albany - SUNY; Maria I Khan, University at Albany - SUNY*

Development and Assimilation of an Ethical Code among Educators. *Ofri Bashan, Bar-Ilan University; Orly Shapira, Tel Aviv University; Jenny Bronstein, Bar-Ilan University*
Implementing Black Student Excellence in K-12 Schools: Structures, Attitudes, and Actions from Three Urban Schools. *Diana A. Porras, California State University - Long Beach; Jolan Smith, California State University - Long Beach; Cara Richards-Tutor, California State University - Long Beach*

Pivot, Zoom, Teach: Adaptive Capacity During times of Social & School Crisis. *Alisun Thompson, University of Puget Sound; Lora Bartlett, University of California - Santa Cruz*
Weaving Belonging in a Time of Crisis: Resilient Schools During and After the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Maria Eugenia Rojas Concha, Pontificia Universidad Catolica de Valparaiso; Carmen Montecinos, Universidad Catolica de Valparaiso; Juan Pablo Valenzuela, Universidad de Chile; Francisco Meneses, Universidad de Chile*

Chair: *Karina Guerrero, Claremont Graduate University*
Discussant: *Jennie Weiner, University of Connecticut*

54.020. Following Policy to Witness the Harms of Epistemic Hierarchy. Division B - Curriculum Studies; Paper Session Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304C; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Boogeyman Politics: A Critical Content Analysis of Indiana's Repeal of Ethnic Studies. *Jasmin Patron-Vargas, Texas A&M University; Lynette O'Neal, Texas A&M University*
Curricular Redlining: Mapping Race, Gender, and Epistemic Hierarchy in New York's Regents Exams (2010-2025). *Tanishia Lavette Williams, Brandeis University*

Scripted Literacy: Power, Perspective, and the Politics of Curriculum in the Elementary Classroom. *Rachel Ranschaert, University of North Texas; Jessica Murdter-Atkinson, University of North Texas*

Strategic Self-Invisibilization as Hidden Curriculum: Ambivalent Belonging of Precarious-Status Youth in Canadian Schools. *Xun Ril Li, University of Toronto - OISE; Dennique Lavia, Justice for Children and Youth; Arlo Kempf, University of Toronto - OISE*

Systemic Erasure Through Interest Convergence: A Critical Reading of Emily Hanford's 'Sold A Story' Podcast. *Ronnie Angel Chavez, Arizona State University; Jeanne M. Powers, Arizona State University*

Chair: *Zachary A. Casey, Rhodes College*

54.021. Knowing Otherwise: Methods, Archives and Educational Research Reimagined through Black Radical Traditions. Division B - Curriculum Studies; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304A;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

- Openings: Breach, Black Liveliness, and the Curriculum-as-Event. *Wilson Kwamogi Okello, Pennsylvania State University*
- Futuring Education Through Archival Praxis. *Chelsea Bouldin, Syracuse University*
- Fashioning New Grammars: Black Posterity, Interdisciplinarity and Critical Educative Spaces. *Brenda Nyandiko Sanya, Colgate University; Durell M. Callier, University of Delaware; Dominique C. Hill, Colgate University*
- Safety for Whom? Black Caribbean Immigrant Youth Negotiating Policing in London and New York Schools. *Derron Wallace, Brandeis University*
- Seeing the Unknown, Sensing the Possible: Unhobbling & CritQuant, A Critical, Creative Literacy Design. *ParKer Bryant, Syracuse University*

Chair: *Malathi Michelle Iyengar, College of San Mateo*

Discussant: *Malathi Michelle Iyengar, College of San Mateo*

54.022. Towards Undisciplining: Temporality, Objects, and Method in Education Research. Division B - Curriculum Studies; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304B;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

- The Overrepresentation of the Normative Science Teacher: An Efficient Entanglement of the Pedagogical Other. *Curtis O'Dwyer, University of Wisconsin - Madison*
- An elementary attempt at undisciplining as method in education research. *Debopam Sen, University of Wisconsin - Madison*
- The Elements of Art and Principles of Design as Governing Tactics of Sight and Self. *Emily Nott, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Christopher M. Kirchgasser, University of Wisconsin - Madison*
- “The Clock Is Ticking”: Undisciplining The Global South Girl and Futurity In International Development Campaigns. *Ramata Diallo, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Chair: *Rachel E. Williams, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Discussant: *Nancy L. Lesko, Teachers College, Columbia University*

54.023. Cognition, Comprehension, Culture, and Cross-Linguistic Transfer: Advancing Equity in Reading Development. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Symposium
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, San Fernando; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Early Reading Growth Across Economic, Linguistic, and Special Education Lines. *Bhabika Joshi, Vanderbilt University; Min Hyun Oh, United States Department of Defense; Phoebe J Ahn, Vanderbilt University; Jeannette Mancilla-Martinez, Vanderbilt University; Gigi Luk, McGill University*

- Multilingual learners' executive functions and reading comprehension: Quasi-experimental evidence from a national sample. *Michael J. Kieffer, New York University; Jeannette Mancilla-Martinez, Vanderbilt University*
- Higher-Order Cognitions in L1 and L2 and Their Relations to Comprehension in Multilingual Learners. *Young-Suk Grace Kim, University of California - Irvine*
- Bridging Language and Literacy for Multilingual Learners: Effects of a Multicomponent Program. *Rebecca Silverman, Stanford University; Patrick Proctor, Boston College; Jeff Harring, University of Maryland; Yukie Toyama, University of California - Berkeley; Annie Camey Kuo, Stanford University; Kristin Keane, Stanford University; Hsiaolin Hsieh, Stanford University; Jackelyn Rivera-Orellana, Stanford University*

Teaching African American Children to Read: Language Variation is an Asset. *Julie A. Washington, University of California - Irvine; Katherine T Rhodes, University of California - Irvine*

Chair: *Patrick Proctor, Boston College*

Discussant: *Gina Biancarosa, University of Oregon*

54.024. Here's The Real Story: Transparent Discussion about Struggles that Underlie Successful Research. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Invited Speaker Session
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Beaudry B; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

- Much Ado About Null-Things: Interrogating the Research Design and Foundational Literature After Unsupported Hypotheses. *Allison Zengilowski, Lehigh University*
- Multiple Journal Rejections in a Row? Welcome to the Club! *Mimi Bong, Korea University*
- Mistakes were Made and Lessons were Learned: Why We Should Always Check the Full Survey Flow. *Allison Master, University of Houston*
- Navigating Advancing Scholarship as a New Mother and Faculty Member. *Elise C. Allen, University of Northern Colorado*
- Schools, Shifts, and Shutdowns: Building Sustainable Research Practice Partnerships for Unpredictable Contexts. *Christine Lee Bae, Virginia Commonwealth University*
- Turning Grant Denials into Data Opportunities: Lessons in Creative Partnerships. *Patrick N. Beymer, University of Cincinnati*
- How Zusho & Clayton Almost Didn't Happen. *Akane Zusho, Fordham University*
- Epistemological Collision and the Cost of Reimagining SEVT

through Race and Power. *Jamaal Matthews, University of Michigan*

Embracing the Organized Chaos of Educational Research. *Patricia A. Alexander, University of Maryland*

Chairs: *Xiao-Yin Chen, University of Tennessee; Korinthia D. Nicolai, Indiana University; Emily Quinn Rosenzweig, Teachers College, Columbia University; Helenrose Fives, Montclair State University*

54.025. Media Comparisons: To Do or Not to Do, That is the Question. Division C - Learning and Instruction;

Symposium

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, San Gabriel A; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Old Questions, Bad Answers: Rejecting Media Comparison Research. *Noah Glaser, University of Missouri*

Do We Really Care About That? *Joshua Weidlich, University of Zurich*

Media Comparisons: Necessary but Currently Not Sufficient. *Amédee Marchand Martella, University of Georgia; Alyssa Lawson, Colby College*

More Nuanced Media Comparisons: Accounting for Complexity Through Moderators and Mediators. *Miriam Mulders, University of Duisburg-Essen*

From Whether to When: Five Conditions for Meaningful Media Comparison Research. *Josef Buchner, St. Gallen University of Teacher Education*

Chairs: *Amédee Marchand Martella, University of Georgia; Alyssa Lawson, Colby College*

Discussant: *Jeff A. Greene, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*

54.026. Promoting Equitable CS and AI Education: Strategies to Expand Capacity and Access. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Structured Poster Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 515A; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

1. Equity in Pennsylvania's Secondary CS Education System: A Longitudinal Study of Student and Teacher Participation (Poster 1). *Robert Schwarzhaupt, American Institutes for Research; Sara Frey, Lancaster Lebanon IU13; Amy E. Trauth, American Institutes for Research; Judd Pittman, Pennsylvania Department of Education*

2. AI by 8: Embedding AI Literacy in K-2 Language Arts in Rural North Carolina Communities (Poster 2). *Joseph P. Wilson, American Institutes for Research; Xuning Cecilia Zhang, American Institutes for Research; Treshonda Rutledge, University of Central Florida; Keisha Bailey, American Institutes for Research; Claire Aguiar, North Carolina State University; Daniel Schmidt, Partner to Improve; Bradford Mott, North Carolina State University; Jessica Vandenberg, North Carolina State University*

3. Teacher Leadership for Expanding Capacity and Access in Statewide Computer Science Education (Poster 3). *Joanna Goode, University of Oregon; Adrienne Pinsonneault, University of Oregon; Casey Emmanuel Tiemann, University of Oregon; Jill Hubbard, Oregon State University - Cascades*

4. Beyond Access: Developing Teacher Capacity to Teach Rigorous Computer Science (Poster 4). *Richard Hill, University of Detroit Mercy; Aman Yadav, Michigan State University; Michael L. Lachney, Michigan State University; Andrew Lapentina, University of Detroit Mercy; Hyein Jee, Michigan State University*

5. Understanding Public K-12 Indigenous Student Interest and Access to CS and AI Education through Teacher Perspectives and National CS Data (Poster 5). *Marissa Spang, American Institutes for Research; Brenda D. Arellano, American Institutes for Research; Joseph P. Wilson, American Institutes for Research*

6. Piloting Professional Development for Indigenous Computer Science (Poster 6). *Jennifer Rosato, University of Minnesota*

7. Statewide Capacity Building To Increase Access in CS Education for Students with Disabilities (Poster 7). *Sara Frey, Lancaster Lebanon IU13; Yi-Cheng Pan, Lancaster Lebanon IU13*

8. Investigating Teacher Perspectives of Data Privacy Related to Computer Science Professional Development (Poster 8). *Joseph C. Tise, Institute for Advancing Computing Education; Monica McGill, Institute for Advancing Computing Education; Robert Schwarzhaupt, American Institutes for Research*

9. Instrumentation for Identifying Areas of Growth for Computer Science Teachers (Poster 9). *Joseph C. Tise, Institute for Advancing Computing Education; Monica McGill, Institute for Advancing Computing Education; Vicky Sedgwick, CSTA; Amanda M. Bell, Computer Science Teachers Association*

10. Pathways into Computing: Equity Trends Among Community College Graduates (Poster 10). *Jinyoung Hur, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

11. Strategies to Build Education-industry Partnerships for Computer Science Education for Rural Elementary Students in Idaho (Poster 11). *Kathryn Rich, American Institutes for Research; Dajung Diana Oh, American Institutes for Research; Mahima Bhattar, American Institutes for Research*

12. Expanding Computer Science Education in Rural Texas: Insights from a Professional Development Program (Poster 12). *Zhuoying Wang, University of Texas at Austin; Miriam Jacobson, University of Texas at Austin; Amy Carrell, University of Texas at Austin*

Chairs: *Robert Schwarzhaupt, American Institutes for Research; Kathryn Rich, American Institutes for Research*

Discussants: *Joanna Goode, University of Oregon; Lien Diaz, Georgia Institute of Technology*

54.027. Rooted in Culture: Teaching Practices Leveraging Black History and Culturally Sustaining Pedagogies in Art, Music, and Dance. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Paper Session

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Palos Verdes; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Preservice Teachers Learn from Jacob Lawrence: Pedagogical Potential in Teaching Black Migration History through Art. *Jeremy Hilburn, University of North Carolina - Wilmington; Donyell L. Roseboro, University of North Carolina - Wilmington*

Culturally Sustaining Pedagogy in Music Education: Music, Media, and Learning Processes from Kid Culture. *Martina Vasil, University of Kentucky*

Generating Culturally Sustaining Pedagogical Strategies through Cross-disciplinary Pláticas. *Juan Andrés Ouviña, Montclair State University; Zakiya Atkinson, California State University - Long Beach*

Unforgetting Our Histories: Embodied, Culturally Sustaining Pedagogies for K-12 Classrooms. *Valerie Ifill, Drexel University; Raja Schaar, Drexel University*

54.028. Scholars as Field Builders: Expanding Pathways for Impact at a Critical Juncture for Education. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Invited Speaker Session

Westin Bonaventure, Level 2, Beverly; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Chairs: *Lisa Quay, Student Experience Research Network; DeLeon Gray, North Carolina State University*

Participants: *Stacey Alicea, Maithreyi Gopalan, University of Oregon; Mary C. Murphy, Indiana University; Gina Ann Garcia, University of California - Berkeley; Marcela G. Cuellar, University of California - Davis; Nathaniel Schwartz, Brown University*

54.029. Student Learning, Reasoning, and Understanding in Mathematics Education. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Paper Session

Westin Bonaventure, Level 3, Avalon; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

An Attentional Choice that Benefits Math Learning: Spontaneously Attending to Relations in Non-Mathematical Settings. *Hongyang Zhao, University of California - Irvine; Ella Rose, University of California - Irvine; Ebrar Aslaner, Bogazici University; Maryam Cheraghi, University of California, Irvine; Lindsey E. Richland, University of California - Irvine*

Cognitive Disequilibrium: The Role of Generative AI in Student Problem Solving. *Katya Hernández Holliday, San Diego State University & University of California, San Diego; Lily Sawi, San Diego State University; Victoria L. Delaney, San Diego State University; Sunday Stein, San Diego State University*

Differential Effect of Prompts on Students' Posed Mathematical Problems and Unexpected Responses. *Hua Ran, Jiangnan University; Jinfa Cai, University of Delaware; Stephen Hwang, University of Delaware*

Global Processing in Subitizing: Eye-Tracking Analysis of High and Low Achievers' Fixation Patterns. *Mona E. Holmqvist, Lund University; Catarina Wåsterlid, Kristianstad University*

Leveraging Technology to Improve Second Graders'

Understanding of Equivalence. *Vivian Hsu, WestEd; Anna N. Bartel, WestEd; Jacklyn Powers, WestEd; Amy Lynn Miyahara, University of Notre Dame; Drew Barrett, WestEd; Jodi Davenport, WestEd; Yvonne Kao, WestEd; Nicole M. McNeil, University of Notre Dame*

Chair: *Ruthmae Sears, University of South Florida*
Discussant: *Elif Tugce Karaca, Kirikkale University*

54.030. AI, Machine Learning, and Data Science in Modeling and Prediction: New Strategies and Applications.

Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Paper Session

InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Los Feliz; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Predicting U.S. Mathematics Achievement in PISA 2022: A Comparative Analysis of Penalized Regression Techniques and Identification of Key Predictors. *Eter Mjavanadze, George Mason University; Angela D. Miller, George Mason University*

Predicting High-Ability Students by Using the Teacher Rating Scale: Insights from Machine Learning and Explainable AI Approaches. *Taeyong Kim, Lewis University; Hyeseong Lee, Lewis University; Ali M. Alodat, Qatar University and Yarmouk University*

Leveraging LLMs on Teacher Voices to Drive Retention Policies. *Angela D. Starrett, University of South Carolina; Svetlana Dmitrieva, University of South Carolina; Brian Cartiff, University of South Carolina*

Clarify the Importance of Tree Numbers in Random Forest Regression. *YaShan Zhuang, East China Normal University; Yi Jiang, East China Normal University*

ADAM estimation for the hierarchical joint model of response accuracy and response time. *Yingshi Huang, University of California - Los Angeles; Minjeong Jeon, University of California - Los Angeles*

Chair: *Ergul Demir, Ankara University*

Discussant: *Jeongwon Choi, Vanderbilt University*

54.031. Division D International Committee Invited Session: Challenges and Opportunities of International Collaboration in the Field of Measurement and Research Methodologies in the AI Era. Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Invited Speaker Session

InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 7th Floor,

Hollywood Ballroom I; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Chair: *Huan Kuang, Florida State University*

Moderator: *Amota Ataneka, University of Cincinnati*

Panelists: *Alina A. Von Davier, Duolingo; Okan Bulut, University of Alberta; Guher Gorgun, IPN - Leibniz Institute for Science and Mathematics Education*

54.032. Mental Health and Help-Seeking Across Cultural Contexts. Division E - Counseling and Human Development; Paper Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 301A;

11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Cultural and Institutional Insights for Suicide Prevention in Higher Education. *Bilge Sulak Akyüz, Bartin University; Beyza Aksu-Dunya, Bartin University; Emir Can Kara, Ka-Ra Counseling Center*

I will be your protector: Black youth mental health & suicide prevention policy. *Rena D. Mayes, University of Arizona; Lauren C. Mims, New York University; Paul C. Harris, Virginia Commonwealth University; Adriana D. Cimetta, University of Arizona*

Mental Health Help-Seeking Among College Students: A 5-Year TPB Analysis. *Yue Zheng, University of Washington; Yonghui Li, East China University of Science and Technology*

Mental Health Help-Seeking Attitudes of Congolese College Students. *Rumbidzai Mushunje, University of North Carolina - Charlotte*

Mental health profiles and help seeking behaviors among community members in the Houston area. *Xin Li, Texas A&M University; Gary Wingenbach, Texas A&M University; Jun Wang, Texas A&M University; Josephine Engels, Mental Health America of Greater Houston; Andrea Usanga, Mental Health America of Greater Houston*

Chair: *Anna Louise Baird, California State University - Dominguez Hills*

Discussant: *Kerstin Marie Cornell, Baylor University*

54.033. Growing, Sharpening and Envisioning Our Tools: The Mapping Carcerality, Imagining Freedom, and (Re)Membering Selves Project. Division G - Social Context of Education; Symposium

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 403A;

11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Mapping Our Selves and Our Embodied Freedom Dreams through the Tree of Life. *Shena Sanchez, University of Alabama; Luis Fierros, Learning Works*

“To Resee, To Refeel, To Rehurt”: How Mora Supports Us to Resight/site/cite Freedom. *Casey Philip Wong, Georgia State University; Mora Greer, Arts for Healing and Justice Network*

“All of ‘em Things I haven’t Felt, I haven’t Seen;” Mapping

Geographies for Collective Liberation. *Miguel Casar, University of Alabama; Ka’Lee Matthews, Arts for Healing and Justice Network*

Curanderxs of Freedom: Learning Practices for Reclamation and Liberation with Youth. *Kevin Hernandez, Arts for Healing and Justice Network; Joaquin Noguera, Loyola Marymount University*

Chair: *Dyoni Isom, Arts for Healing and Justice Network*

Discussant: *Lindsey Eichenberger, Arts for Healing and Justice Network*

54.034. Imagining and Enacting Indigenous Futures: Sovereignty, Self-Determination, and Education. Division G - Social Context of Education; Symposium

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 303A;

11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Woven with Unconditional Love: Reweaving Healing through Ancestral Pathways and Memory. *Kelly Leah Stewart, University of California, Los Angeles*

Indigenous Educational Sovereignty and Culturally Responsive, Sustaining, and Revitalizing Pedagogies: A Seven-Generations View. *Bryan McKinley Jones Brayboy, Northwestern University; Teresa L. McCarty, University of California - Los Angeles*

Imagining Indigenous Futures through the Enactment of Linguistic Sovereignty – Wisdom from Indigenous-Language Education. *Tiffany S. Lee, University of New Mexico; Sheilah E. Nicholas, University of Arizona; Teresa L. McCarty, University of California - Los Angeles; Michael H. Seltzer, University of California - Los Angeles; Kyle Halle-Erby, University of California - Los Angeles; Thomas Jacobson, University of California - Los Angeles; James McKenzie, University of Arizona*

I Pa‘a Ke Kahua Kumu: A Generational Legacy of Educational Sovereignty in Hawaiian-Medium Teacher Education. *Keiki Kawai‘ae‘a, University of Hawai‘i at Hilo; Makalapua Alencastre, University of Hawaii at Hilo*

Pedagogical Self-Determination and Indigenous Futures: Remembering and Remaking Kin in Territories Currently Marked Urban. *Megan Bang, Northwestern University; Anna Lees, University of Washington; Ananda M. Marin, University of California - Los Angeles*

Chairs: *Bryan McKinley Jones Brayboy, Northwestern University; Teresa L. McCarty, University of California - Los Angeles*

Discussant: *Amanda R. Tachine, University of Oregon*

54.035. Queer Male Teachers of Color in the Social Context of Education VP Session. Division G - Social Context of Education; Paper Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 501C;

11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Because of Mr. Baldwin: The Fire of Power and the Work of

Liberation. *Jarvais J Jackson, Indiana University Indianapolis*

Who does the Service Work? Comparing Trans Men Educators of Color in Schools to Trans Women and Nonbinary Educators. *Mario I Suárez, Utah State University*

An Autoethnography of a Gay Latino Scholar Navigating Academia and Social Studies Education. *Edgar Díaz, Utah State University*

Invisible at the Intersection: Queer Men of Color, Cultural Media, and Education. *Roland Sintos Coloma, Wayne State University*

Chair: *Cleveland Hayes, Indiana University - Indianapolis*

Discussant: *Cleveland Hayes, Indiana University - Indianapolis*

54.036. Studying Black Students in Context. Division G - Social Context of Education; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 511C;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Black Joy as a Neo-Emotion: A Systematic Literature Review of Black Joy in Educational Contexts. *Erin Nicole Cox, University of Michigan*

Drawn, Filmed, and Heard: Youth Participatory Research With Gifted Black Girls in White Spaces. *Oriana T. Leach, Chapin Hall Center for Children at the University of Chicago*

Examining Various Forms of Violence Target at Black Women and Girls in Educational Spaces. *Stephanie Renee Anckle, City of Long Beach*

What Gets Measured Gets Studied: A Review of Dataset Use in Research on Black Students. *Imani Dixon, University of California - Los Angeles; Jada Sims, University of California - Los Angeles; Neven Matthew Holland, University of California - Los Angeles; Jaylen Lowe, UCLA*

Discussant: *Nathan Alexander, Howard University*

54.037. The Sankofa Research Intensive (SRI): A Fugitive Space for Scholars Centering Black Children In Research. Division G - Social Context of Education; Symposium

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 403B;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

A Love Letter to Black Women in the Academy: Lessons from the Sankofa Research Intensive. *Bisola A. Wald, University of Minnesota; N'Dyah McCoy, University of Miami; Keara L. Williams, University of California - Los Angeles; Sophia Wells-Williams, George Mason University; Kayla Miller, Clemson University; Shemiyah Holland, University of California - Santa Barbara; Erica B. Edwards, Wayne State University*

Centering Blackness and Jegnaship: An Africana Governance Framework to Support Black Women Doctoral Students in Predominantly White Institutions. *Yvette Latunde, University*

of La Verne; Courtney Wilkerson, Howard University

Moving from Mentoring to Jegnaship: Reconceptualizing HOW we Engage Black Women in the Academy. *Kimberly L. King-Jupiter, Alabama State University*

Aesthetic Mentoring, Sisterhood, and Respectability Politics. *Ashley N. Woodson, Black epiSTEMologies*

Chair: *Rema E. Reynolds Vassar, Wayne State University*

Discussant: *Linda C. Tillman, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*

54.038. Critical Considerations for Faculty Careers in the US and Abroad. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum G; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Beyond the Written Word: Unpacking the Hidden Labour of Academic References in Postgraduate Admissions. *Bowen Zhang, Durham University*

Bodies in Tension: Chilean Theater Faculty's Academic Performance in the Face of Research Policies. *Marisol Campillay Llanos, Universidad las Américas*

Containment Listening: Theorizing the Interactional Choreography of Care That Neutralizes Critique in Trust-Based Academic Relationships. *Shahnaz Masani, Michigan State University*

Navigating the Academic Tower: A Quantitative Ethnography of Faculty Perceptions of Counteroffers in Higher Education. *Catherine L. Zhang, University of Pennsylvania; Dennis Espejo, University of Pennsylvania; Ivana Marshall, University of Pennsylvania; Damani K. White-Lewis, University of Pennsylvania*

Who Gets More? Analyzing Counteroffer Quality Across Faculty Demographics and Ranks. *Dennis Espejo, University of Pennsylvania; Damani K. White-Lewis, University of Pennsylvania; Catherine L. Zhang, University of Pennsylvania; Ivana Marshall, University of Pennsylvania*

Chair: *Catherine L. Zhang, University of Pennsylvania*

54.039. Navigating the Politics of Retrenchment in Higher Education: Four Senior Scholars Reflect B(l)ack.

Division J - Postsecondary Education; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum H; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Navigating Research Agendas Centered on Black Life in the Academy. *Lori Patton Davis, University of California, Los Angeles*

Scholars Teaching, Researching, and Consulting in DEI: Applying Lessons Learned. *Darin M. L. Stewart, University of Denver*

Realizing Aspirations, Career Growth, and Advancement During Moments of Retrenchment. *Joy Gaston Gayles, North Carolina State University*

Color-evasive Repression: DEI Rollbacks and the Logic of Legitimation. *Eboni M. Zamani-Gallaher, University of Pittsburgh*

Chair: *Eboni M. Zamani-Gallaher, University of Pittsburgh*
Discussant: *Eboni M. Zamani-Gallaher, University of Pittsburgh*

54.040. Promise Fulfilled? The Transfer of College Credits Earned in High School. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum F;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

College Credit Accumulation in High School and Linkages to Postsecondary Success. *Christine Mulhern, RAND; Brian M. Phillips, RAND Corporation; Michelle Bongard, RAND Corporation; Cristina Alvarez, RAND Corporation*

Experiences with Transferring College Credits Earned in High School. *Laura Rosof, University of North Carolina - Greensboro; Tiffany Lee Smith Tovey, University of North Carolina - Greensboro*

Unlocking College Momentum: How Transferring College Credits Earned in High School Relates to Postsecondary Outcomes. *Brian M. Phillips, RAND Corporation; Christine Mulhern, RAND; Michelle Bongard, RAND Corporation*

Using Transcript Data to Examine Credit Applicability: Methodological lessons learned. *Holley Nichols, North Carolina State University*

Chair: *Julie A. Edmunds, University of North Carolina - Greensboro*

Discussant: *Lauren Schudde, University of Texas at Austin*

54.041. A Rallying Cry: Sustaining Equity-Centered Teacher Preparation in Light of TQP Grant Terminations. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 2;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Reconstructing Equity-Focused Teacher Preparation Through Federal Grant Termination. *A. Dee Williams, California State University - Los Angeles; Leila Ansari Ricci, California State University - Los Angeles; Kimberly A. Persiani, California State University - Los Angeles; Marco A. Nava, Los Angeles Unified School District*

Preparing to Serve: The Ripple Effects of Terminating a Middle School Teacher Residency. *Imelda Nava-Landeros, University of California - Los Angeles; Theodore Ruiz Sagun, University of California - Los Angeles; Emma D. Hipolito, University of California - Los Angeles*

Evaluating Teacher Quality Partnerships: The Importance of Teacher Workforce Data in Advancing Educator Preparation and Policy. *Jaclyn J. Tejwani, WestEd; Selena Cartznes, WestEd*

UnINSPIREd: Uncertain Futures in the Wake of Grant Termination. *Jessica Jensen, California Polytechnic State*

University - San Luis Obispo; Andrea F. Somoza-Norton, California Polytechnic State University - San Luis Obispo; Stephen Crutchfield, California Polytechnic State University - San Luis Obispo; Natasha Neumann, California Polytechnic State University - San Luis Obispo

Chair: *Briana Ronan, California Polytechnic State University - San Luis Obispo*

Discussant: *Annamarie M. Francois, University of California - Los Angeles*

54.042. Critical Perspectives on Grading, Tutoring, and Justice in Schools. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 7;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Examining Perceptions of K-12 Grading Practices Among Undergraduate Seniors and Implications for Teacher Preparation Programs. *Leo W. Cavinder, Indiana University; Laura J. Link, University of North Dakota; Janet R. Decker, Indiana University*

Promoting Equity for Disadvantaged Students through One-to-One Tutoring. *Mustafa Ozcan, MEF University; Sude Sozen, MEF University; Servet Altan, MEF University*

Hands-on, Hearts-In: Cultivating Effective Special Educators Through Immersive Experiential Learning. *Pui Pui Phoebe Cheung, Yew Chung College of Early Childhood Education*
“I hate that I didn’t know this”: Pre-service teachers’ reflections on learning to evade imperialism. *Nesrin El-Isa, Michigan State University; Alexandra Allweiss, Michigan State University; Shireen Al-Adeimi, Michigan State University*

Chair: *Laura J. Link, University of North Dakota*

Discussant: *Denisse Maribel Hinojosa, Texas Tech University*

54.043. Reimagining Language Teaching: Wellness, Identity, & Equity in Professional Learning. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 8;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Bridging Language and Content: How K–12 Teachers Reimagine Translanguaging Through a Virtual Workshop. *Yixin Zan, George Mason University; Sujin Kim, George Mason University; Dai Gu, George Mason University; Bilgehan Ayik, George Mason University; Woomee Kim, George Mason University*

Building Trauma-Informed Readiness in Preservice Teachers for Refugee Multilingual Learners Through Workshop Intervention. *Jihee Im, Washington State University*
Effects of World Language Professional Learning on Teacher Practice and Wellness. *Margaret Peterson, Stanford University; Amado M. Padilla, Stanford University; Xinjie Chen, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Elizabeth*

Matchett, Stanford University; Eduardo Rafael Munoz-Munoz, San José State University

The Differences between New-service and Experienced Teachers' Linguistic Practices in a Community of Practice. *Nan Jiang, University of Arizona; Laurel Hendrickson, University of Arizona*

Two Transnational Teachers' Journey to Becoming Critically Conscious Educator for Black Dual Language Learners. *Mingzhu Deng, Georgetown University; Sabrina L. Wesley-Nero, Georgetown University*

Chair: *Kenneth J. Varner, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*

Discussant: *Kenneth J. Varner, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*

54.044. Implementing Justice: Race-Conscious Policy Futures and the Practice of Educational Equity. Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 9;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Critical Policy Analysis: Navigating Policy In/Coherence and Examining State-District Policies Impacting K-12 Equity-Centered Leadership. *Maria Del Carmen Unda, University of Texas at Austin; Estela Lopez, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Kait Ogden, University of Texas at Austin; Jacob Navarrete, University of Texas at Austin; Joshua Childs, University of Texas at Austin; Ain A. Grooms, University of Wisconsin - Madison; April L. Peters-Hawkins, University of Houston; Eligio Martinez, Cal Poly Pomona*

“Democratizing” PTO Data for Racial Equity: Investigating Pathways to Challenge PTO Inequities. *Brittany C. Murray, Davidson College; Claire Mackevicius, University of Oregon*

Fiscal Bureaucrats as Policy Implementation Actors: How School Business Officials Navigate Educational Equity Through Resource Allocation. *Sandra Emmanuella Okonofua, Yale University*

Implementation of State Mandated Culturally-Relevant and Sustaining Education Training in k-12 Districts in Pennsylvania. *Christopher G. Pupik Dean, University of Pennsylvania; Sarah Anne Eckert, Eastern University; Luca Poxon, Temple University; Patricia M. Joergensen, Holy Family University; Aaron Johnson, Teach Plus*

Race-Conscious Futures and Educational Justice: Transforming Human Rights Policy Implementation in Ontario's K-8 Schools. *Shezadi Khushal, University of Toronto - OISE*

Chair: *Vincent D. Willis, University of Alabama*

Discussant: *Jawanza Kalonji Rand, Teachers College, Columbia University*

54.045. The Architecture of Education Governance: Institutions, Leadership, and Influence. Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 10; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

From Policy to Pavement: Boots on the Ground in State Takeover Territories. *Quinci Bone't Teer, Cleveland State University*

Re-imagining California's County Offices of Education. *Althea Ito, University of California - Berkeley; Kurt Klaus, University of California - Berkeley; Jose Eos Trinidad, University of California - Berkeley*

Understanding the Landscape of State Education Agencies. *Sierra Stern, University of Pittsburgh*

Promoting Equity amid Shifting Political Contexts: A Multi-State Case Study. *Hannah Goldstein, University of Pittsburgh; Hayley Ryan Weddle, University of Pittsburgh; Megan Hopkins, University of California - San Diego*

Fractured Alliances: The Evolution of School Choice Advocacy Coalitions in the Era of School Vouchers. *Huriya Jabbar, University of Southern California; Julie A. Marsh, University of Southern California; Desiree O'Neal, University of Southern California; Hanora Tracy, Tulane University*

SIG Sessions

54.046. Critical Issues in Action Research: Immigrant & Refugee Education, Ethnic Studies, Teacher Quality, Community, and Indigenous Youth. SIG-Action Research; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 1;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Aprendiendo Adentro con la Migra Afuera: Immigrant & Refugee Education Amidst State-Sanctioned Violence. *Micaela Bronstein, University of California - Los Angeles*

From Classroom to Community: K-12 Ethnic Studies for Community Engagement. *Edward Flores, California State University - Northridge*

Parsing out Teacher Quality in Youth Participatory Action Research. *Praveen K Dubey, Montana State University Northern; Angela Crevar, Mercer University; Mattius Rischard, Montana State University - Northern*

Preparing and Supporting Youth for Meaningful Research Involvement: Recommendations from Community-Based Participatory Research. *Amanda Sommerfeld Case, University of Iowa; Yiheng Zhou, University of Iowa;*

Shahnaz Safitri, Purdue University; Yinmayue Tang, University of Iowa; Viviana Piceno, Purdue University; Remi Napier, Downtown Boxing Gym; Keenan Cain, Martin Luther King Jr. High School; Garrett Simmons, University of Detroit Jesuit High School; Jamarion Berry, University of Detroit Jesuit High School; Aleena Watson, Regina High School

Youth Participatory Action Research with Indigenous Youth: A Scoping Review. *Kate Somerville, University of Wisconsin-*

Madison; Natalie Behnke, University of Virginia; Kate Joshua, University of Virginia; Lora Henderson Smith, University of Virginia

Chair: Krisanna L. Machtmes, Ohio University

54.047. Child Development Across Varied Contexts. SIG-

Adolescence and Youth Development; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 301B;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Adolescent-Centered Compassion: Aligning Curriculum with Developmental Needs through Co-Design. *Blake A. Colaianne, Pennsylvania State University*

Associations of School-Level Racial Diversity, Student Belonging, and Attendance as Mediated by Social Safety Perceptions. *Bradley Crimmins, University of Illinois at Chicago; Ting Dai, University of Illinois at Chicago*

Designing With, Not For: A Case Study of Neurodivergent STEM Learners' Identity, Agency, and Presence. *Amy Walter, North Carolina State University; Briana Trager, North Carolina State University; Bruce Graham, North Carolina State University; Jessica H. Hunt, North Carolina State University; Krista D. Glazewski, North Carolina State University*

Parents' Intervention In Chinese Young People's Gaming Behaviours And Family Relationship. *Dajun Wang, University of Glasgow*

Professional Learning in Youth Development That Empowers Educators and Produces Positive Youth Outcomes. *Sirocus Barnes, Georgia Institute of Technology; Charmaine Davis-Grant, Department of Education and Workforce (DEW); Edlyn Lauren Thompson-Mettle, Stevens Institute of Technology*

Chair: Michael J. Seaberry, Clark Atlanta University

54.048. AI for Equity, Access, and Innovation in Postsecondary Writing and Learning Contexts. SIG-Advanced

Technologies for Learning; Symposium
Westin Bonaventure, Level 2, Mt. Washington; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Advancing Systematic Literature Review Methods Using Artificial Intelligence. *Elnara Mammadova, Purdue University*

AI-Driven Writing Pedagogies in MSI Classrooms: Enhancing Digital Literacy, Equity, and Student Engagement. *Shahin Hossain, University of Maryland - Baltimore County; Md Mahmudul Haque, North Dakota State University*

Cheating or Learning? A Descriptive Case Study on the Use of Generative AI in Academic Research. *Samaa Haniya, Pepperdine University; Aasiyah Ghazi, Pepperdine University*

Leveraging Artificial Intelligence to Foster Literacy Motivation Among Students Struggling to Read. *Temidayo Jaiyesimi,*

University of Kentucky; Meenu Devi, University of Kentucky
AI, Communication, and Accessibility: A Scoping Review on Deaf/Hard-of-Hearing Learners with Learning Disabilities. *Juliana Hirn, University of Central Florida*

Chair: Meryem Mekouar, Florida International University
Discussant: Reyna G. Garcia-Ramos, Pepperdine University

54.049. From Margins to Momentum: Honoring Over 30 Years of Korean DLBE for Linguistic Justice. SIG-

Bilingual Education Research; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 506;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Parents' Views on Bilingual and Biliteracy Development in KDLBE Programs. *Hakyoon Lee, Georgia State University; Shim Lew, University of West Florida*

Teacher Perspectives in a Korean Dual Language Bilingual Education Program in a Georgia Elementary School. *Jayoung Choi, Kennesaw State University*

Envisioning Possibilities: The Case of Korean-English Dual Language Bilingual Education in Illinois. *Chaehyun Lee, Southeastern Oklahoma State University; Woongsik Choi, Illinois State University*

Paving the Way: Leadership for Korean Dual Language Programs. *Jongyeon Joy Ee, Loyola Marymount University; Minhye Son, California State University - Dominguez Hills*

Chairs: *Jongyeon Joy Ee, Loyola Marymount University; Minhye Son, California State University - Dominguez Hills*

Discussant: *Jin-Sook Lee, University of California - Santa Barbara*

54.050. Seeing Teaching Clearly: New Approaches to Classroom Observation and Feedback. SIG-Classroom

Observation; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Georgia I;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Classroom Observations and Formative Feedback to Teachers – Validating a New Instrument to Assess Instructional Quality. *Christopher Kellermann, Freie Universität Berlin; Holger Gärtner, Freie Universität Berlin; Anabel Bach, Free University - Berlin; Bilge Gencoglu, University of Groningen; Katharina Holder, Freie Universität Berlin; Annette Vogt-Daldrup, Freie Universität Berlin; Felicitas Thiel, Freie Universität Berlin*

Online Versus In-Person Science Instructional Practices: Classroom Observations in Rural Settings. *Henan Zhang, Texas A&M University; Andrea McMurray, Texas A&M University; Cindy L. Guerrero, Texas A&M University; Rafael Lara-Alecio, Texas A&M University; Beverly J. Irby, Texas A&M University; Fuhui Tong, Texas A&M University*

Reciprocal Peer Observations: Giving and Getting Feedback on Formative Assessment Practices. *Caroline Wylie, Center for Assessment; Eowyn P. O'Dwyer, Rutgers University;*

Christine Lyon, Formative Solutions

The Teacher Observation Protocol For 3D-Science (TOPS): A New Instrument For 3D-Science Implementation And Improvement. *Clara Smith, Brigham Young University; Heather Leary, Brigham Young University; Lane Fischer, Brigham Young University; Josh Stowers, Brigham Young University; Rebecca Sansom, Texas A&M University*

54.051. Centering Blackness in Teacher Education Institute.

SIG-Critical Educators for Social Justice; Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 303B; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Chairs: *Freyca Calderon-Berumen, Pennsylvania State University - Altoona; Dyanis Conrad, Randolph-Macon College*

Presenters: *Shamaine Bertrand, The College of New Jersey; Kisha M Porcher, University of Delaware*

54.052. Collaboration, Harmony, Attention & Acomedido:

Learning Strengths among Mexican and Indigenous Peoples of the Americas. SIG-Cultural-Historical Research; Symposium

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, La Brea; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Inclusive Collaboration and Harmony – Between Researchers and Mayan Research Participants. *Barbara Rogoff, University of California - Santa Cruz; Itzel Aceves-Azuara, California State University - Sacramento*

Third-Party Attention Across Generations of Guatemalan Mayan Children. *Itzel Aceves-Azuara, California State University - Sacramento; Barbara Rogoff, University of California - Santa Cruz; Katie G. Silva, University of California - Santa Cruz*

The primacy of the common good: Mapuche children collaborating to achieve a learning goal in a science classroom. *Paula Alonqueo, University of La Frontera*

Do College Students Collaborate Differently? A Cultural Lens on Latino and European American Group Work. *Itzel Aceves-Azuara, California State University - Sacramento; Amanda Maria Lopez, California State University, Sacramento; Mariana Lara, California State University - Sacramento*

Chair: *Itzel Aceves-Azuara, California State University - Sacramento*

Discussant: *Andrew Dayton, University of Southern California*

54.053. Anti-Diversity, Repression and Neo-Mercantilism : Can Global Citizenship Education Survive? SIG-

Democratic Citizenship in Education; Symposium

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum I; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

A North American Perspective Based on Grassroots Global

Citizenship Education in the United States. *Theresa Alviar Martin, Kennesaw State University*

An Asian Perspective Based on the Current Status of Global Citizenship Education in China. *Zhenzhou Zhao, Education University of Hong Kong*

An African Perspectives on the Current Status of Global Citizenship Education in North Africa. *Amanda B. Richey, Kennesaw State University*

An African Perspectives Based on the Current Status of Global Citizenship Education in Western Africa. *Nuru Akinyemi, Kennesaw State University*

A European Perspective on the Current Status of Global Citizenship Education. *Wiel M. Veugelers, University of Humanistic Studies Utrecht; Jan Gube, The Education University of Hong Kong*

Chair: *Kerry J. Kennedy, The Education University of Hong Kong*
Discussant: *Kerry J. Kennedy, The Education University of Hong Kong*

54.054. Pedagogical Practices and Classroom Quality in Early Learning. SIG-Early Education and Child Development;

Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Georgia II; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

From Fantasy to Function: Children's Perceptions of a Robotics-Infused Play-Based Curriculum. *Monica Miller Marsh, Kent State University; Iyanuoluwa Emmanuel Olalowo, Kent State University; Sumyea Jashim Benta, Kent State University - Kent*

Understanding Preschool Children's Composing Development: Attention to Relevance, Language, and Cohesion. *Yanfang Zeng, Texas A&M University; Tianshu Yang, Texas A&M University; Hope K. Gerde, Texas A&M University; Gary E. Bingham, Georgia State University; Margaret F. Quinn, Texas A&M University*

Early Childhood Science Teaching Practices and Children's Inquiry Skills. *Rebecca Elizabeth Sermenon, University of Idaho; Shiyi Chen, University of Idaho; Kathryn Hodge, University of Idaho; Zoe Froh, University of Idaho*

Chair: *Hope K. Gerde, Texas A&M University*

Discussant: *Myae Han, University of Delaware*

54.055. Supporting Youth Activism in Hostile Times: Case Studies in Deepening YPAR Practices. SIG-Grassroots

Community and Youth Organizing for Educational Justice; Structured Poster Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 515B; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

1. Broadening Research Methods and Deepening Analysis in Youth Participatory Action Research (Poster 1). *Dane Stickney, University of Colorado - Denver; Carlos P. Hipolito-Delgado, University of Colorado - Denver; Shelley*

Zion, Rowan University

2. Youth Learning Outcomes from Youth Participatory Action Research: A Practical Assessment (Poster 2). *Ben Kirshner, University of Colorado - Boulder; Carlos P. Hipolito-Delgado, University of Colorado - Denver; Salvador Ramirez, University of Colorado - Boulder*
 3. Transformative Student Voice Experiences for Elementary School Students: Building a Foundation for Changemaking (Poster 3). *Julissa Ventura, Marquette University*
 4. Brown & Black Girl Leadership through a Critical Race Feminist Lens (Poster 4). *Carla Cariño, Denver Public Schools; Nayeli Lopez, University of Colorado - Boulder*
 5. Arts-Based Inquiry as Resistance: Elevating Student Voices Through Collage Methodology (Poster 5). *Idalis Kizee, Rowan University*
 6. Student Resistance and the Curriculum: Youth Participatory Action Research as Resistance through Transformative Action (Poster 6). *Jordana Simmons Berwise, Rowan University; William A. Rozycki, Rowan University; Crystal Hutchinson, Rowan University; Jamar Durelle Brownlee, Rowan University; Shelley Zion, Rowan University*
 7. Contemporary Problems of Practice in YPAR: Research, Policy & Storytelling (Poster 7). *Daniela Krueh DiGiacomo, University of Kentucky; Chase Colvin, Kentucky Student Voice Team; Arivumani Srivastara, Claremont University - Claremont McKenna College*
 8. Teaching in Solidarity: Toward Critical Youth Research Literacies (Poster 8). *Brian Mooney, Fairleigh Dickinson University*
 9. Learning in Solidarity: A YPAR Study of International Student Belonging & Activism (Poster 9). *Sadhay Pharaiz Nunez, Fairleigh Dickinson University; Samantha Anil Figaro-Olivo, Fairleigh Dickinson University*
 10. Reading in Solidarity: Resisting the Curricular Status Quo with Palestinian Youth & Literature (Poster 10). *Rashida Mustafa, Teachers College, Columbia University*
 11. Y-PARChiving & Localized Histories: Building Youth-Driven Curriculum in NYC (Poster 11). *Shreya Sunderram, Graduate Center - CUNY*
- Chairs: *Yolanda Sealey-Ruiz, Teachers College, Columbia University; Marlo A. Reeves, Independent Consultant*
Discussants: *Limarys Caraballo, Teachers College, Columbia University; Monica Gonzalez Ybarra, University of Illinois*

54.056. Co-Composing A Music of the Oppressed Framework; A Critical, Cultural and Creative Resistance YPAR Offering. SIG-Hip Hop Theories, Praxis & Pedagogies; Workshop
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum E; 11:45am to 1:15pm
Chair: *Martin Urbach, Graduate Center - CUNY*

54.057. Mind, Awareness, and Pedagogical Practice. SIG-Holistic Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 6; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Awareness and the Limits of Abstraction: A Kantian Meditation on Pedagogy, AI, & Perception. *Raaghav Pandya, City University of New York; Punya Mishra, Arizona State University*

Innovating East-West Integrated Liberal Education: Optimizing the Evaluation System in BNBU's Whole Person Education Model. *Ash Lu Chen, Columbia University*

Toward a Theory of Holistic Wellbeing in Higher Education. *John Yang, UCLA*

Chair: *Sosanya M. Jones, Howard University*

Discussant: *Ida Oberman, Alanus University of Arts and Social Sciences*

54.058. Video Interaction Analysis Lab: Working Processes as Relation Building in Times of Unrest. SIG-Learning Sciences; Working Group Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 501A; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Analyzing in Community: The Generous and Generative Nature of Lab Relationships. *Erica Lee Payne, Vanderbilt University; Tessaly Jen, Vanderbilt University*

Expanding Multiplicities as Warrants for Claims in Interaction Analysis. *Candice Love, University of Maryland*
"Welcome back to our channel!" – Reframing the Role of the Camera in Video Research. *Lana Cosic, Vanderbilt University; Sarah Jaewon Lee, University of Washington*
Interaction Analysis in Conversation with a Radical Black Politics of Visuality. *Natalie Annabelle Rae, Pennsylvania State University*

Engaging with the Hidden Record: Surfacing the Felt and More-Than-Human in Video Analysis. *Lana Cosic, Vanderbilt University; Tessaly Jen, Vanderbilt University*

Chair: *Lana Cosic, Vanderbilt University*

Discussants: *Kate Chapman; Bethany Daniel, Vanderbilt University*

54.059. "Bad Mentor": Community Perceptions of "Qualified" Mentors in the Tower and the Block. SIG-Mentorship and Mentoring Practices; Symposium
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Los Feliz; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Behind the Baton: The Double-Bind of Mentorship, Isolation, and Ethical Care in Secondary Music Education. *Andrew Dutch, University of Colorado - Denver*

Pain We Inherit and Harm We Pass On: Rethinking Mentorship Through a Holistic Critical Lens. *Michael A. Hunt, University of Maryland - Baltimore County*

Devil Was Never Who They Said It Was: Poetic Inquiry, Mentorship, and the Violence of Institutional Care. *Darius*

Phelps, Cuny

“Wakey, wakey, biatch!”: Spooky’s Lessons on Critical Mentorship. *Robin Brandehoff, University of Colorado - Denver*

Chair: *Robin Brandehoff, University of Colorado - Denver*
Discussant: *Aaron J. Griffen, DSST Public Schools*

54.060. Global Perspectives on Digital Storytelling for Identity, Justice, and Community. SIG-Narrative Research; Symposium

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum J; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Cultivating Mathematical Identity Through Digital Storytelling: Indonesian Teachers' Journey of Professional Growth.

Angga Hidayat, Universitas Pamulang

(Re)Storying Our Mathematics Identity through Comics:

Nigerian Girls’ Narratives in a Transnational Study. *Ruth Nneoma Oliwe, The Ohio State University*

Digital Storytelling as Epistemic Resistance: Asian American Youth Reimagining Narrative and Belonging. *Fuyi Feng, The Ohio State University*

Mathematical Wonder in Early Years: Digital Storytelling for Teachers to Support Young Children's Mathematical Exploration. *Nurmalia Nurmalia, Rumah Cahaya Empat Ribu*

Superhero Mathematics: Immigrant Youth Creating Counter-Narratives of Mathematical Power. *Theodore Chao, California State University - Fullerton*

Bridging Continents and Classrooms: A Cross-National Study of Mathematical Storytelling in University Settings. *Zareen Aga, James Madison University; Paul Hernandez-Martinez, Loughborough University; Sayonita Ghosh Hajra, Sacramento State University*

Chair: *Theodore Chao, California State University - Fullerton*
Discussant: *Zareen Aga, James Madison University*

54.061. Supporting Student Learning in Online Settings. SIG-Online Teaching and Learning; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, San Gabriel B; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Exploring Tutoring Strategies and Dropout Patterns in Online Math Learning via Big Data and LLMs. *Gokhan Gulfidan, University of Utah; Chenglu Li, University of Utah; Bailing Lyu, University of Utah; Linlin Wu, University of Utah*

Exploring Expert and Peer Tutoring Dynamics in Online Learning Discussions: A Temporal Learning Analytics Approach. *Wanli Xing, University of Florida; Zifeng Liu, University of Florida*

Combating Summer Learning Loss with Online Learning: A 10-State Study. *Xiaozhu An, IXL Learning; Huan Liu, IXL Learning; Christina C Schonberg, IXL Learning; Bozhidar M. Bashkov, IXL Learning*

Learning Profiles in Hybrid Learning Environments:

Metacognitive Awareness, Approaches to Learning, and Study-Related Burnout. *Katri Johanna Koivuneva, University of Lapland; Anna Parpala, University of Helsinki; Telle Hailikari, University of Helsinki; Heli Ruokamo, University of Lapland*

A Framework of Online Discussions to Guide the Design, Development, and Facilitation of Online Learning. *Patrick R. Lowenthal, Boise State University; Kristen McHenry, Boise State University; Anthony C. Saba, Boise State University*

Chair: *Kimberley L. Chandler, Johns Hopkins University*

54.062. Ethnodrama and Research-based Theatre in Theory and Performance. SIG-Qualitative Research;

Demonstration/Performance

InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Echo Park; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Ethnodrama as Research Genre: A Narrative and Dialogical Typology. *Andrew Babson, University of Pennsylvania*

Friends for Life: The Power of Experience, Story, and Performance. *Charles F. Vanover, University of South Florida*

The Cost of Triumph: Translating Narrative Research in Cabaret for Arts-Based Education Inquiry. *Candace Marie Henry, University of South Florida*

In Search for Balanced Identity. *Marianna Glynska, Independent Scholar*

Chair: *Charles F. Vanover, University of South Florida*
Director: *Rijul Kataria, The Yuva Ekta Foundation*

54.063. Black Feminist Participatory Action Research to Challenge Hegemonic Cultures at Predominately Black Institutions. SIG-Research Focus on Black Education; Off-Site Site

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 504; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participant:

Black Feminist Participatory Action Research to Challenge Hegemonic Cultures at PBIs Activity Response Document. *Simone Nicholson, Tufts University*

54.064. Separate and Unequal: Studying Title IX in an Era of Extreme Conservative Backlash. SIG-Research Focus on Education and Sport; Symposium

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Beaudry A; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Advancing Leadership Development for Female College Athletes: Disrupting Gendered Inequities in College Sports. *Sarah E. Stokowski, Clemson University*

“What Can I Do, What Can We Do?”: Exploring Black Women College Athletes’ Racial Justice Activism and Engagement

During and After 2020. *Ezinne Ofoegbu, Santa Clara University; Briana Savage, University of California - Riverside*

Gender segregation vs. semi-segregated: Two approaches to governing intercollegiate athletics, neither of which achieve parity. *Kirsten Hextrum, Oregon State University*

Chair: *Kirsten Hextrum, Oregon State University*

Discussants: *Jennifer L. Hoffman, University of Washington; Valyncia C. Raphael-Woodward, University of Southern California*

54.065. Perspectives on Student Belonging and Humanization in Mathematics Classrooms. SIG-Research in Mathematics Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum A; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Broadening Perspectives and Participation: Five Factors that Contribute to Mathematical Belonging. *Cindy Jong, University of Kentucky; Pooja Sidney, University of Kentucky; Benjamin Braun, University of Kentucky*

Mathematics Teacher Educators' Self-Study: Integrating Rehumanizing Mathematics and Professional Noticing with Elementary Teacher Candidates. *Naomi Jessup, Georgia State University; Crystal A. Kalinec Craig, University of Texas - San Antonio; Cindy Jong, University of Kentucky; Molly H. Fisher, Rowan University; Segun Timothy Ajose, University of Kentucky; Jonathan Norris Thomas, University of Kentucky; Anh Pham, University of Texas - San Antonio; Emily Bonner, University of Texas - San Antonio*

Social-Emotional Learning and Mathematics Achievement: The Role of Teacher- Student Relationship, Stress Resistance, and Emotion Control. *Xijing Wang, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Melissa Dan Wang, The Education University of Hong Kong*

Teaching Practices that Promote Mathematical Wellbeing in Elementary Learners. *Tye Campbell, Utah State University; Erin Rich, Indiana University; Sehrish Jabeen, Utah State University; Melissa S. Barker, Utah State University; Mindy Green, Revere School*

The Influence of Students' Value Fulfillment on Mathematical Wellbeing. *Erin E. Rich, Indiana University; Tye Campbell, Utah State University; Mindy Green, Revere School*

Chair: *Mogege David Mosimege, University of the Free State*

Discussant: *Charles E. Wilkes, University of California - Davis*

54.066. Developing Psychosocial Skills. SIG-Research on Giftedness, Creativity and Talent; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Level 2, Echo Park; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

"More Than Grades": The Hidden Power of Peer Relationships in Gifted Adolescents' Well-Being. *Fangfang Cai, Johns Hopkins University; Keri M. Guilbault, Johns Hopkins*

University

Motivation and Academic Achievement in K–12 Advanced Learners: A Meta-Analysis of Expectancies and Values. *Maryann R. Hebda; Tracey N. Sulak, Baylor University*

Profiles of Hope in Gifted Turkish Adolescents: Associations With Psychosocial and Academic Outcomes. *Ilke Bayazitli, University of California - Berkeley; Linsey B. Cohen, University of California - Berkeley; Hetvi Desai, University of California - Berkeley; Golzar Ejadi, University of California - Berkeley; Mark B. Pommer, University of California - Berkeley; Carlos Isaac Rivera, University of California - Berkeley; Raymond Quang Vo, University of California - Berkeley*

Using History as A Mirror: Understanding the Covid-19 Pandemic's Impact on Gifted Students. *Fangfang Mo, Purdue University; Yao Yang, Purdue University; Yuxiao Zhang, Purdue University*

STEM Identity of Underrepresented Gifted Youth: A Qualitative Case Study. *Tugce Karatas, Purdue University; Nielsen Pereira, Purdue University/Gifted Education Research & Resource Institute; Jack William Ev Weston, Purdue University*

Chair: *Christopher J.P. Sewell, Colorado College*

Discussant: *Del Siegle, University of Connecticut*

54.067. Trenzando Chicana Latina Feminist Perspectives into Mathematics Education. SIG-Socio-Political Issues in Mathematics and Science Education; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum D; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Formas de Vivir: Latina Mothers as Co-Constructors of Knowledge. *Susana Beltran-Grimm, Portland State University*

Building Mutual Trust Through Pláticas: Relational Approaches to Research Practice Partnerships in Early Childhood. *Daniela Alvarez-Vargas, Colorado State University*

Pláticas Across Terrains: Navigating Institutional Whiteness in Mathematics Education. *Sabrina Zarza, Michigan State University*

Revealing Our Work, Their Stories, and Historical Contexts Through Composite Counter-storytelling. *Stacy Jones, University of Texas - San Antonio*

Chairs: *Sabrina Zarza, Michigan State University; Sandra Zuniga, San José State University*

Discussant: *Rochelle Gutierrez, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

54.068. Reimagining Policy and Practice in Special Education: Practices, Systems, and Equity. SIG-Special and Inclusive Education Research; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum C; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Supplementary Aids and Services in State Special Education Policy: Consistency or Confusion? *James C. Coviello, St. John's University; Reva Mathieu-Sher, Duquesne University; Joseph A. Hogan, Kean University*

Changing What Schools Do: The Promise and Complexities of Transforming Social Systems for Students with EDs. *Christine Park, New York University; Natalie May, New York University; Elizabeth Blair Cox, New York University; Elise Cappella, New York University; Michelle Flemen-Tung, New York University*

A Critical Policy Analysis of "Extra Time": Disability, Time, and Power in U.S. Special Education Policy. *Maya Berrol-Young, Teachers College, Columbia University; Jasper W. Golden, Teachers College, Columbia University*

"The Placement is Individualized, But the Barriers Are Systemic": Child Study Team Perspectives on Inclusive Education. *Jessica Ann McQueston, Sam Houston State University; Joseph A. Hogan, Kean University; James C. Coviello, St. John's University; Cristin Montalbano, New Jersey Coalition for Inclusive Education*

Breaking Barriers and Building Access: Educator Insights on Intersectional Special Education for Multilingual Learners. *Kathryn A. Brooks, Butler University; Suneeta Kercood, Butler University; Catherine Bhatena, Indianapolis Public Schools*

Chair: *Emilee A Baker, University of Minnesota*

54.069. Digital Professionalism and Immersive Technologies in Teacher Education and Practice. SIG-Technology as an Agent of Change in Teaching and Learning; Paper Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum B; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Why Pre-Service Teachers Don't Use Social Media: Prerequisites and Reasons of Non-Users. *Hermann Dzingel, University of Potsdam; André Meyer, University of Potsdam; Eric Richter, KU Eichstätt-Ingolstadt; Dirk Richter, University of Potsdam*

The Impact of Social Media on K-12 Teachers' Perceptions of Their Profession: An Experimental Study. *Victoria Puglia, Massachusetts Department of Elementary and Secondary Education; Suzanne E. Graham, University of New Hampshire; Jeffrey P. Carpenter, Elon University*

Integrate Virtual Reality in Science Education: An Ethnographic Case Study of Faculty and Students/Pre-service Teachers Experiences. *Wei Wu, California State University - Fresno; Xiaojun Chen, St. John's University; Amanda Klassen, California State University - Fresno; Theresa White, California State University - Fresno*

Chair: *Nazanin Adhami, University of Florida*

Discussant: *Bret Staudt Willet, Florida State University*

54.070. Educators and AI: Perspective, Practice, and

Professional Growth. SIG-Technology as an Agent of Change in Teaching and Learning; Paper Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 3; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Artificial Intelligence in Teacher Professional Development: A Systematic Review. *Nick Erhardt, University of Potsdam; Eric Richter, KU Eichstätt-Ingolstadt; Yizhen Huang, University of Potsdam; Dirk Richter, University of Potsdam; Katharina Scheiter, University of Potsdam*

First-Year Teachers Navigating Generative Artificial Intelligence: A Culturally Responsive Teaching Perspective. *Eun Kyung Ko, National Louis University; Vishodana Thamocharan, National Louis University*

Pedagogical Unforgetting Through Red-Teaming: How Adversarial AI Engagement Transforms Teacher Identity and Practice. *Devan Walton, University at Albany - SUNY; Jaesung Park, University at Albany - SUNY; Yingru Zhao, University at Albany - SUNY; Haesol Bae, University at Albany - SUNY*

Chair: *Amanda Banks, East Tennessee State University*

Discussant: *Diane Codding, University at Albany - SUNY*

54.071. Critical and Embodied Literacies: Narrations of Unforgetting by Intergenerational Women of Color. SIG-Writing and Literacies; Symposium JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Atrium II; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Do Not Grow Weary: Wholehearted Dimensions of Unforgetting. *Jessica Reed, Michigan State University*
Unforgetting Black Literacies: Historical Embodied Practice Beyond School Walls. *Chelsea Jimenez, University of South Carolina Beaufort*

Affirming Identity & Sustaining Students' Sense of Self. *Adrianna Foadare, Colgate University*

Unforgetting: A Promise Worth Keeping. *Camilla J. Bell-Ferdinand, Colgate University*

The Battle of Self-Exploration. *Kylee Lopez, Colgate University*
ESL: Erased, Silenced, Labeled. *Amanda Escalona, Colgate University*

Chair: *Jessica Reed, Michigan State University*

Discussant: *Camilla J. Bell-Ferdinand, Colgate University*

Division and SIG Roundtables

54.072. AERA Roundtable Session Friday 11:45 am;
Roundtable Session

54.072-1. Preparing Principals for Complexity: Equity, Crisis, and the Future of Leadership Learning (Table 1).
Division A - Administration; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D;

11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Preparing and Developing Equitable Leaders in the Event of a School Shooting. *Joanne M. Marshall, Iowa State University; Douglas M. Wieczorek, Iowa State University*

Rehearsing for the Revolution: Theater of the Oppressed as a Tool for Liberatory Leadership Education. *Bryan J. Duarte, Purdue University; Érica Fernández, Miami University (OH)*

Unprepared to Lead: Examining How Limited Special Education Training Impacts Campus Administrators and Instructional Leaders. *Carrie Anna Mitchell, University of Texas - San Antonio*

What is Known About Principals' Professional Learning?: Characterizing the Literature Since No Child Left Behind. *Morgaen L. Donaldson, University of Connecticut; Jessica G. Rigby, University of Washington; Jason A. Grissom, Vanderbilt University; Elizabeth Rose Farnham, University of Connecticut; Michael Martin, University of Connecticut; Stephanie R. Forman, University of Washington; Michelle Doughty, Vanderbilt University*

Chair: *April M. Stokes, Montclair State University*

54.072-2. Historicizing Equity Since the Era of Desegregation

(Table 2). Division F - Historical Inquiry in Education; Roundtable Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Towards a Post-Brown v. Board of Education Life Course Framework: Historically Grounding Education-Health Scholarship. *Collin Perryman, Arizona State University*

Unforgetting Majority-to-Minority Histories: Racial Politics in Local Southern Schools. *Matthew Shiloh, Georgia State University; Chara H. Bohan, Georgia State University*

The Haunting of Hope: Unforgetting the Demolition of Ravenswood High School. *Antonio D Lopez, Stanford University*

Lessons from Building a Living Archive: Teacher Learning Through Practitioner Inquiry into Black Philadelphian Histories. *Barrett Rosser, Morgan State University; Kyra Williams, University of Pennsylvania; Bonnee Breese Bentum, School District of Philadelphia; Njemele Anderson, The School District of Philadelphia; Antoine Stroman, School District of Philadelphia; Angela Crawford, The School District of Philadelphia*

A Mismatch of Ends and Means: Progressive Education and School Inequity in 1960s West Philadelphia. *Edward M. Epstein, University of Pennsylvania*

Chair: *Callie Avondet, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

54.072-3. Memory as Method in Education: Policy Histories, Community Pedagogies, and Liberatory Futures (Table 3). Division F - Historical Inquiry in Education; Roundtable

Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D;

11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Policy Tensions of Institutionalized Student-Initiated Outreach at UCLA for Communities of Color: A Historical Ethnography. *Michelle Velasco, University of California - Los Angeles*

Negotiating Morality: Teaching and Archiving the Struggle for Comprehensive Sex Education in the Post-Roe Era. *Gabriela G. Corona Valencia, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Reclaiming the Archives of Lennox: Community Memory, Critical Pedagogy, and Educational Belonging. *Edwin Leonidas Rivera Castellanos, University of California - Riverside*

Letters to Learn By: Epistolary-Based Pedagogy for Honoring Memory and Voice in the College Classroom. *Cindy R. Escobedo, University of California - Los Angeles*

Chair: *Brenda Y. Lopez, California State University - Fullerton*

Discussant: *Corinna D. Ott, University of California - Riverside*

54.072-4. Musicking Normal Schools: Soundings of Capital, Gender, Race in Past, Current, Futures of Teacher Education (Table 4). Division F - Historical Inquiry in

Education; Roundtable Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

The Music Course Offerings, Degrees, and Certifications of Twelve American Normal Schools. *Lori F. Gray, University of Montana*

Mary McLeod Bethune and the Rise of Music Education at the Daytona Normal and Industrial. *Roger Anderson, Central State University*

Music Education at the Eastern Illinois Normal School. *Danelle Larson, Eastern Illinois University*

Choral Ensembles in American Normal Schools: Comparing Performance Offerings across Four Institutions, 1871–1926. *Dawn M Farmer, Augustana College*

Remapping Jazz Teaching and Learning in Postsecondary Schools—Normal School Jazz: 1920s to the 1940s. *Keith Brenden Kelly, Arizona State University*

Instrumental Music in American Normal Schools: A Historical Overview of Ensembles, Instruction, and Inclusion. *Jill M. Sullivan, Arizona State University*

Chair: *Jill M Sullivan, Arizona State University*

Discussant: *Marie F. McCarthy, University of Michigan*

54.072-5. Our Presence Is Not Inevitable: Reflecting on Chicana/o Interventions at The University of California (Table 5). Division F - Historical Inquiry in Education;

Roundtable Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D;

11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Pedagogies of the Movement: Chicano Public Art as Educational Praxis. *Gloria E. Poveda, California Northstate University*

From El Plan De Santa Barbara to an HSI, What it Means to Serve Chicano/Latino Students Across Time and Place.

Arlene Cano Matute, University of California - Riverside

The Latino Eligibility Taskforce: A Strategic Intervention to Expand the Latina/Latino Educational Pipeline into the University of California. *Fernando Peña, University of California - Riverside*

Chair: *Tara J. Yosso, University of California - Riverside*

Discussant: *Tara J. Yosso, University of California - Riverside*

54.072-6. Identity and Culture (Table 6). Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Reflections on Identity and Culture: Using Multimodal Literacies to Reimagine Histories, Selves, and Communities. *Catherine Park, University of California - Berkeley; Glynda A. Hull, University of California, Berkeley*

Memeing Yeshiva University: Community Cultural Wealth on Instagram at an Orthodox Jewish University. *Lindsay Metzker-Epstein, Temple University*

Entanglements, Englishes, and Transraciolinguistic Becoming: Navigating Coloniallingualism Across Borders. *Dianne T. Wellington, SUNY - College at Cortland; Yetunde S. Alabede, Michigan State University; Andrew A. Hunte, University of the West Indies - Five Islands; Taiwo Jumoke Ogundapo, Indiana University; Patriann Smith, University of South Florida*

Exploring Multimodal Expression of Taíno Worldviews and Perspectives through a Multiliteracies Transpositional Grammar. *Martha Rosas, Lehman College - CUNY*

Chair: *Erika Abarca Millán, New York University*

54.072-7. The Agency of Language (Table 7). Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Understanding the Relationship between Multidimensional Poverty and Early Language Development in Rural China.

Ling Li, Southwest University; 俞萱李, Southwest University; Li Huang, The Southwest University of China

A scoping review of research on adolescents' multilingual literacy in schools. *Thea Williamson, Old Dominion University; Brielle Donlan, Old Dominion University*

Educator Perspectives About the Science of Reading for English Learners' Literacy in VPK-Grades 3. *Vassiliki*

Zygoris-Coe, University of Central Florida; Laila Noor, University of Central Florida; Marjorie Ceballos, University of Central Florida; Florin Marius Mihai, University of Central Florida; Leslie Dugger Carvajal, University of Central Florida

Additive Bilingualism, Community Cultural Wealth, and Program Design: The Case of Project R.A.I.C.E.S. *Marisol Diaz, California State Polytechnic University - Pomona; Chrissy J Cross, Stephen F. Austin State University; Heather K. Olson Beal, Stephen F. Austin State University*
Chair: *Aya M. Isaac, University at Albany - SUNY*

54.072-8. Linguistic Justice and Policy Implications for Multilingual Learners (Table 8). Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Re-Visiting the Past, Re-Imagining the Future: Interrogating California's Teacher Performance Expectation 7 for Linguistic Justice. *Devanshi Unadkat, San Diego State University; Monica Baldonado-Ruiz, San Diego State University; Sera Jean Hernandez, San Diego State University*

Navigating a Shifting Policy Landscape: English Language Proficiency Test Exemptions in U.S. Higher Education. *Gertrude Arthur, University of Missouri; Edwin Nii Bonney, Clemson University; Augustine Owusu Achiaw, Clemson University; Kafayat Amoke Adesina, Clemson University*

Systematic Review on Consequential Validity for English Language Learners (ELLs) Post-2015 by Examining Classifications. *Maria Pia Oelrich, College of William & Mary; David Davenport, College of William & Mary*

Widening the Gate? Inclusive Identification Policies and Multilingual Learner Access to TAG. *Janette Dalila Avelar, University of Oregon*

Chair: *Kelly Ann Peña, Rutgers University*

54.072-9. Teacher's Work in Contentious Times: Policy and Organizing (Table 9). SIG-Teachers Work/Teacher Unions; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

The Finance that Can Determine Materials Conditions of Teachers' Work. *David Isaac Backer, Seton Hall University*
Critical Discourse Analysis of Quality in Early Care and Education: Navigating Politicized Landscapes. *Erin K. West, Appalachian State University*

Interview with Lois Weiner: Dangers and Possibilities for Public Education. *Lois Weiner, New Jersey City University; Abby C. Emerson, Touro University*

Celebrating Educators of Color: A Radical Disruption of the Status Quo. *Amira Nash, University of Iowa; Monique*

Cottman, Iowa City Community School District

54.072-10. Frameworks of Empowerment: Enabling Youth and Families to Take Action through Out of School Time Experiences (Table 10). SIG-Out-of-School Time;

Roundtable Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Beyond Limits: Empowering Children with Disabilities Through Inclusive Martial Arts Practices. *Jess Mueller, Arizona State Board of Education*

Cultivating Latine Empowerment in STEM: How Culturally Responsive Mentor Strategies Foster Empowerment in After-School Programs. *Stella Kiyomi Rabago, University of California - Irvine; Taylor Michelle Wycoff, University of California - Irvine; Guadalupe Rosas, University of California - Irvine; Sandra D. Simpkins, University of California - Irvine*

Puentes Familiares: Facilitating Family Partnership in Out of School Time. *Amy Vatne Bintliff, University of California - San Diego; Ashley Yung Batchelor, Arizona State University; Rogelio Becerra Songolo, University of California - San Diego; Itzel Gonzalez Velazquez, University of California - San Diego; Sayra Martinez, La Colonia De Eden Garden Inc; Aylin I Paez, University of California - San Diego; Ernesto Orozco, University of California - San Diego*

Discussant: *Miranda M. Allen, Texas Tech University*

54.072-11. Global Crossroads: Policy, Pedagogy, and Innovation in Asian Education Systems (Table 11).

Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Becoming in the Cracks: Teachers' Lines of Practice in the Implementation of China's Bi-Transition Policy. *Shuoqi Song, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

Decolonizing Education in Taiwan: An Asian-Tribal Critical Race Theory Analysis of Indigenous Experimental Education. *Yang Ming (Albert) Chen, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

Organizational Competencies and Policy Recommendations for Developing Provincial Education Offices in Thailand's Deep South. *Ekkarin Sungtong, Prince of Songkla University; Warapark Maitreephun, Prince of Songkla University; Recha Choosuwana, Prince of Songkla University*

Chair: *Jie Lin, Shanghai Jiao Tong University*

Discussant: *Eujin Park, Stanford University*

54.073. AERA Roundtable Session Friday 11:45 am - Gold 1;
Roundtable Session

54.073-1. Roundtable Session 4: Student Learning and Development in College and Beyond (Table 1). Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Exploring Core Competencies as Predictors of Global Competency Among Undergraduate Students. *Junseo Kim, Korea University; Yejeong Jenny Park, Seoul National University; Yewon Kim, Ewha Womans University; Heewon Lee, Seoul National University; John Jongho Park, Pennsylvania State University*

Speaking Up, Feeling Seen: Creating Culturally Affirming Classrooms. *Kiya Ma, University of Kansas*

Structural mechanisms of educational aspirations of working-class students in elite universities in China. *Qi An, The University of Hong Kong*

Success of Internship: Interns' 'fitting-in' Strategy and Organizational Orientation Activities. *Yin Yue Lam, The Education University of Hong Kong; Jiafang Lu, The Education University of Hong Kong; Jianjing Tang, The Education University of Hong Kong*

Tracking the Pulse: Intensive Longitudinal Study of Student Engagement and Contextual Correlates in Higher Education. *Pin-Cheng Huang, National Yang Ming Chiao Tung University; Meng-Ting Lo, National Yang Ming Chiao Tung University*

54.073-2. P-20 Pipeline Models and Practices for Student Success (Table 2). Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

From College-for-all to Career Readiness: A Comparative Policy Analysis of Shifts in National School-to-Work Reforms. *Donatus Doe, University of Delaware*

Repairing the K-12 to College Pipeline Post-COVID-19. *Susan Suh, Pepperdine University; Kathleen Scott, Pepperdine University; Keaton Kirkwood, Pepperdine University; Ryan C. Weber, Pepperdine University; Alvin Suh, Pepperdine University*

From Aspiration to Occupation: STEM Career Pathways Through Community Colleges. *Johyun Kim, Texas A&M University; Heesun Kim, Texas A&M University; Jungmin Lee, University of Kentucky*

Chair: *Jase Kugiya, University of Texas at Austin*

54.073-3. Teacher Leadership and School Change: Influencing, Negotiating, and Innovating (Table 3). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Exploring Elementary Mathematics Specialists' Opportunities for Teacher Leadership: Negotiating Strategies and Interpersonal Forces. *Carla Lynn Tanguay, Georgia State University; Susan Swars Auslander, University of Alabama; Gary E. Bingham, Georgia State University; Debra Fuentes, Brigham Young University*

Teacher Leadership as a Multidimensional Mediator: Linking School Climate to Instructional Innovation. *Seoyeon Park, University of Nevada, Las Vegas; Peter Wiens, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*

The Development Status and Influencing Factors of Teacher Leadership in China and the U.S. *Chen Xie, East China Normal University*

Chair: *DaShaunda Patterson, Georgia State University*

54.073-4. Rooted and Rising: Latinx Educators Reimagining Belonging and Citizenship (Table 4). Division K -

Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Pathways into Teaching: Uncovering the Narratives of Beginning Teachers from a Hispanic Serving Institution. *Erika L. Mein, University of Texas - El Paso; Angelica Monarrez, University of Texas - El Paso; Jennifer Stefania Herrera Lozano, University of Texas - El Paso*

Reliving Prop 227: Bilingual Latinx educator trajectories amid conditional citizenship. *Annette Beauchamp, University of Minnesota; Ramon Vasquez, University of Minnesota*

"Rooted in Tlatohcān Epistemologies: Bridging Latina/o Pedagogies and Families through the Praxis of Cariño." *Ana Isabel Carrasco, The University of Texas at Austin; Dora Diaz, University of Texas at Austin*

We're Still Here: Queer Latino Teachers Reimagining Citizenship and Visibility Amid Legislative Backlash. *Steven R. Montemayor, Austin Community College; Delandrea Hall, University of North Texas*

Chair: *Erika L. Mein, University of Texas - El Paso*

54.073-5. Unforgetting and Reimagining: Teacher Identities Across Languages and Contexts (Table 5). Division K -

Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Becoming Otherwise: An Autoethnography of Language Teacher Education, Emotion, and Institutional Disobedience. *Jessica Selleck, Buffalo Public Schools*

Culturally Situated Teacher Identities: Identity Construction of CFL Teachers in U.S. Higher Education. *Chang Liu, AERA*

Language Teacher Professional Development from Perezhivanie Lens across Teaching Career Stages: A Systematic Literature Review. *Triubaida Maya Ardianti, The*

Ohio State University; Lutfi Ashar Mauludin, The Ohio State University

Unforgetting the Past and Imagining Futures of Bilingual Teachers in Mathematics: A LatCrit Approach. *Weverton Ataide Pinheiro, Texas Tech University; Ufomanefe Shola Kayode, Texas Tech University; Bernard J. Wekullo, Texas Tech University; Romario Montaña-Ramos, Texas Tech University; Linnie Greenlees, Texas Tech University; Elyssa Cherry Shive, Texas Tech University; Joseph L. Leyva, Texas Tech University; Steven Colmus, Texas Tech University; Delia Carrizales, Texas Tech University; Fernando Valle, Texas Tech University*

Chair: *Triubaida Maya Ardianti, The Ohio State University*

54.073-6. Reframing Teacher Growth: Simulation, Mentorship, and Online Learning for a New Era (Table 6). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education;

Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Building Teacher Confidence and Practice in Older Students' Foundational Literacy: Asynchronous Online Professional Learning Findings. *Claire E. Delcourt, Teachers College, Columbia University; Diana Cordova-Cobo, Student Achievement Partners*

D.E.S.I.G.N. Coaching: A Relational Framework for Reflective, Data-Informed Practice in K-12 Education. *Krishna Belino Cart, The George Washington University*

From Recipients to Co-Creators: How Teacher-Researcher Collaboration Transforms Professional Identity in Limited Resources Context. *Sarah Fitri, University of Cambridge; Nurani Fitriana, SMP Mamba'Unnur Bululawang; Fais Fauziah, SMP Negeri 1 Pagelaran; Yeni Istiyani, SMPN 1 Dampit; Novi Dwi Maria Ulfa, SMP Al Falah Al Makky Gondanglegi Malang; Teguh Budiarto, SD Negeri 3 Dadapan*

Unforgetting Mentorship Traditions to Reimagine Teacher Futures: Mixed-Method Analysis of Microteaching Lesson-Study for Transformative Practice. *Sherone A. Smith-Sanchez, Molloy University; Audra Cerruto, Molloy University; Rickey Moroney, Molloy University; Kirsten Watts, Molloy College; Jeanne Kimpel, Molloy University; Rebeca Herrero Saenz, Molloy University; Devi Singh, Molloy University; Sonia Singh, Molloy University; Samantha Di Stefano, Molloy University; Stephanie Marie Sage, Molloy College*

Chair: *Merve Basdogan, Texas Tech University*

Discussant: *Allie J. Boquet, Louisiana State University*

54.073-7. Participation and Power: Global Perspectives on Voice and Rights in Education Governance (Table 7).

Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

“Sugar Dissolved in Water” – Ideological Constructions and Contestations of Critical Thinking in China’s Quality-oriented Education Reform. *Yan Xie, University of Auckland; Joanna R. Smith, University of Auckland; Maree Davies, University of Auckland*

Evaluating State-School-Family (In)congruence in the Root Causes and Approaches to Reduce Absenteeism. *Monica Flamini, Governor’s Office of Student Achievement; Shuyang Wang, The Governor’s Office of Student Achievement (GA); Tiyanna Peterson, Michigan State University; Jerome Graham, Michigan State University; Daphne M. Penn, Vanderbilt University; Richard O. Welsh, Vanderbilt University*

“Now It Feels Like Faceless Corporations”: Public Sentiment About the Elimination of Elected School Boards. *Sachin Maharaj, University of Ottawa; Meg Garrard, University of Ottawa*

“They’re Taught To Hate America”: Trumpism, Fear, And Framing Educators As Enemies Of The State. *Caryn M. Calisi, University of Texas at San Antonio*

54.073-8. Classroom (Mis)management and the Ecologies of Place: The Role of Teachers in School Discipline (Table 8). SIG-Classroom Management; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

His Behavior Makes Me So Angry: Teacher Education Students’ Mindsets and their Attributions of Classroom Behavior. *Nicole L. Lorenzetti, City College of New York - CUNY*

The impact of TEA program on teaching practices of the Secondary EL Teachers of Bangladesh. *Md Tozammel Haque, Northern Illinois University*

Interpersonal Attributions of Common Classroom Behavior: Validating a Vignette Survey Instrument. *Nicole L. Lorenzetti, City College of New York - CUNY; Alexandra Bloshenko, City College - CUNY*

Supporting Classroom Management Learning Through App-Based Reflection in Student Teacher Internships. *Tom Adams, KWIC*

Understanding the Impact of Universal Tier 1 Supports for Students: A Meta-Analysis of Academic, Behavioral, Social, and Emotional Outcomes. *Yuemeng Wang, University of Connecticut; Jinwei Song, Queens College; Qingqing Du, Nanyang Technological University - National Institute of Education; Tobey Doble Moore, University of Connecticut; Brandi Simonsen, University of Connecticut*

Chair: *Nicholas E. Mitchell, University of Kansas*

Discussant: *Sheree Nicole Alexander, Atlantic City School District*

54.074. AERA Roundtable Session Friday 11:45 am - Gold 2;
Roundtable Session

54.074-1. Digital and Media Spaces of Critical Connection (Table 1). SIG-Media, Culture, and Learning; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Animating Equity: Using Popular Films for Transformative Dialogue in K-12 Settings. *Charlotte Rainey Parham, University of Central Arkansas; Donna Wake, University of Central Arkansas*

Exploring Identity, Engagement, and Opportunity: The Educational Impacts of Esports in K–12 School Contexts. *Paige Littlefield, University of Oklahoma; Danny Mattox, University of Oklahoma; Leslie A. Williams, University of Oklahoma; Linda Atkinson, University of Oklahoma*

Youth Designing Socio-Ecological Futures: Reworlding Game Ecologies. *Edward Rivero, Teachers College, Columbia University; Arturo Cortez, University of California - Davis*

Exploration As Relationship: Native Youths’ Explorations With Digital Technologies for Storytelling. *Chasity H. Mayo, Utah State University; Dallas Haws, Utah State University; Christina Morgan, Utah State University; Tifiny Mills, Utah State University; Eileen Quintana, Nebo School District; Analysa Allison, Nebo Title VI Indian Education; Natalie Billie, Nebo Title VI Indian Education Program; Breanne K. Litts, Utah State University*

Chair: *Amir Michalovich, University of Manitoba*

54.074-2. Exploring Impacts of Human and Technology Interconnectedness (Table 2). SIG-Media, Culture, and Learning; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

A Multimodal Engagement Matrix to Assess the Quality of YouTube Read-Alouds for Young Children. *Margaret F. Quinn, Texas A&M University; Amanda Yoshiko Shimizu, Eastern Kentucky University*

Loneliness, Instagram Use, and Their Impact on Learning among University Students. *En Pei Huang, National Yang Ming Chiao Tung University; Ziting Li, National Yang Ming Chiao Tung University; Meng-Ting Lo, National Yang Ming Chiao Tung University*

The Machine as Storyteller: Posthumanism, AI-Generated Video, and Disrupted Meaning-Making. *Md Mamunur Rashid, University of Rochester*

Chair: *Alexandra Panos, University of South Florida*

54.074-3. Exploring Tensions and Agency in Media Literacy (Table 3). SIG-Media, Culture, and Learning; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Assessing the Synthetic Media Literacy Skills of Undergraduate Students. *Samia Alkam, University of California - Riverside*
Critical Media Literacy in Motion: Chinese International Students Negotiating Transnational Media. *Huan Gao, University of Memphis; Nuo Xu, Bowling Green State University*

Media Literacy, Privacy Concerns, and Parenting Efficacy: The Mediating Role of Child-Rights-Respecting Parenting among Korean Parents. *Kibong Yun, Sejong Cyber University; Seulki Ku, Erikson Institute*

Chair: *Stephanie Rollag Yoon, Minnesota State University - Mankato*

54.074-4. AI in Early Childhood: Posthuman Perspectives on Digital Practices Across Children's Geographies (Table 4). SIG-Media, Culture, and Learning; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Reconfiguring the Classroom: Entanglements of In-service Early Childhood Educators and AI as a Subversive-feminist Force in the Postdigital Assemblage. *Jaye Johnson Thiel, University of Alabama*

Prompt Literacies and Affective Companions: First Graders Thinking↔Feeling With AI. *Bessie P. Dernikos, Florida Atlantic University*

"Before Google Replies.....": Conversational Assistants in the Homes of Very Young Children in the UK. *Julia Gillen, Lancaster University; Sabina Savadova, University of Edinburgh*

"Please Just Ask Me.": Aware and Intentional Use of Digital Images of Children. *Lisa K Kervin, University of Wollongong*

Chair: *Jaye Johnson Thiel, University of Alabama*

Discussant: *Danielle M. Carrier, University of Southern Mississippi*

54.074-5. Identities Intersecting and Crossing Boundaries in Digital Spaces (Table 5). SIG-Media, Culture, and Learning; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Keeping Up with K-pop: Translingual Participation of Anglophone Fans across Digital Boundaries. *Suok Kwon, Stetson University*

Literacies Lived Through Digital Making. *Layla Coleman, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Social Media Addiction and Mental Health: The Mediating Role of Mindfulness. *Felix Kruse, St. Gallen University of Teacher Education; Arvid Nagel, PH-Institute NMS Bern*

Creative Assemblages Beyond Borders: Cosmopolitan Literacies and AI-Mediated Storytelling. *Ahram Park, University of Utah*

54.074-6. Implications of Public Opinion from Media Spaces Toward Education and Equity (Table 6). SIG-Media, Culture, and Learning; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Framing the Narrative: A Qualitative Analysis of Social Media Platforms' Approaches to Media Literacy and Misinformation. *Danielle R. Brown, Florida Atlantic University; Jillian Powers, Florida Atlantic University*

Understanding Public Opinions toward AI in Education: A Cross-Platform Discourse Analysis of Social Media Comments. *Ceren Gokmen, Texas Tech University*

Understanding the De-professionalization of Teaching: Is Representation in Social Media Constructing the Problem? *Danielle T Ligocki, Oakland University; Martha Wilkins, Lewis University*

Unmasking the Reel Gatekeepers: A Critical Analysis of Black Ownership, Distribution Equity, and Institutional Power in Hollywood Film. *Charles Opong, Loyola Marymount University*

Chair: *Cherise McBride, Stanford University*

54.074-7. New Framings for Critical Media Research (Table 7). SIG-Media, Culture, and Learning; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Gamified Affordances and Green Behavior on Ant Forest. *Shitian Qu, Beijing Normal-Hong Kong Baptist University; Yi Ronald Ding, Beijing Normal-Hong Kong Baptist University; Kun Fu, Beijing Normal-Hong Kong Baptist University; Yating Wang, Beijing Normal-Hong Kong Baptist University; James Yang, Beijing Normal-Hong Kong Baptist University*

Postdigitalism and Ecopedagogy: Contested Terrains. *Greg William Misiaszek, Tohoku University*

Reframing Imagination in Educational Games: A Systematic Review Using Critical Theory and Indigenous Perspectives. *Jennifer Sutcliffe, Michigan State University*

Sensory-Inscribed Embodiment, Distraction, and "Disembodiment": A Critical Research Domain. *S. Otto Khera, New Mexico State University*

Chair: *Richard V. Kahn, Antioch University*

54.074-8. Students' Meaning Making with Media Literacy (Table 8). SIG-Media, Culture, and Learning; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

- Measuring Adolescents' Fake News Literacy Based on Evaluation Performance Regarding Simulated News Posts. *Jun Xie, University of Hong Kong; Frank Reichert, University of Hong Kong*
- Navigating Digital Realities: Understanding Young People's Engagement with Social Media Texts. *Rachel Besharat Mann, Wesleyan University*
- Wikipedia Hesitancy as an Obstacle to Civic Online Reasoning. *Christopher Donnan Gravelle, CUNY Graduate Center; Patricia J. Brooks, Graduate Center - CUNY; Arshia K. Lodhi, Graduate Center - CUNY; Kyler Cromer, Hunter College; Donna Scimecca, College of Staten Island - CUNY*
- "The Silo Effect": A Mixed Methods Exploration of a 7th Grade Digital Citizenship Curriculum. *Kathy Chau Rohn, University of New Hampshire; Adam M. McCreedy, University of Connecticut; Jennifer Phaiah, Sacred Heart University; Kelly Farrell, UConn*

54.074-9. Connecting the past, present, and future: Reclaiming play and literacy for all children (Table 9). SIG-Critical Perspectives on Early Childhood Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

- Co-Constructing Democracy in Play: Kindergarten Children's Civic Participation in a Structured Role Simulation. *Qiming Liu, University of Cambridge*
- Communicative Belonging: Reclaiming Early Literacy through Translanguaging and Black Language Pedagogy. *Mariana Souto-Manning, Erikson Institute; Ayesha Rabadi-Raol, Sonoma State University; Jessica Martell, Teachers College, Columbia University; Patty Pion, New York City Department of Education*
- Literacy in the In-Between: A postcolonial re-reading of early literacies in Bangladesh. *Moutushi Mahreen, Pennsylvania State University*
- Play as Justice: Designing Liberatory Play Worlds with Generative AI in Early Childhood Education. *Michelle DeJohnette, Cal Poly Pomona*
- Unruly Literacies: Young Children's Digital Documentation as Meaning-Making and Resistance. *Andrea Sanchez, Kent State University*

Chair: *Kerry H. Alexander, University of Maryland*

54.075. AERA Roundtable Session Friday 11:45 am - Gold 3; Roundtable Session

54.075-1. From 'SPED' to Solidarity: Unforgetting Exclusion and Imagining Disability-Just Futures in K-12 Education (Table 1). SIG-Disability Studies in Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;

11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

- Concrete Utopias and Crip Futurities: Reimagining Special Education through Blochian Hope. *Joseph R Passi, Purdue University Northwest*
- Imagining different spaces and times: Experiences of children with disabilities in India. *Tanushree Sarkar, University of Missouri*
- The Discursive Construction and Governance of Inclusive Education in China: A Critical Discourse Analysis. *Ning Ning, University of Jinan-China*
- The Makings of a Disability Justice Team: An Exploratory-Workshop. *Dave White, University of Nevada - Reno; Randall Owen, University of Nevada - Reno*
- They called me 'Es stupido,' and 'SPED': Ability Segregation and the Dark Side of Academic Intervention. *Martha Perez-Mugg, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*
- Chairs: *Nisha Acharya Julien, Opportunity Consulting; Eleanor Xiaoxiao Mehta, St. John's University*

54.075-2. (Re)Imagining Language, Identity, and Belonging Across Transnational Contexts (Table 2). SIG-Language and Social Processes; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

- Language Use and Identity Construction of an Adolescent Chinese Immigrant. *Yuhan Gao, The Ohio State University*
- Positioning the Past, Imagining the Future: Chinese Mothers' Discursive Constructions of Caregiving Identity. *Chunru Dong, University of Maryland; Jennifer Danridge Turner, University of Maryland*
- Brokering Invisible Borders: Understanding Gatekeeping Interactions between International Graduate Students and Local Immigrant Populations. *Betsy R. Rymes, University of Pennsylvania; Sydney Negus, University of Pennsylvania*
- Transnational Literacies: A Literature-Based Exploration of Family-Led Heritage Language Maintenance. *Deepshikha Banerjee, Boston College*
- Chair: *Munira Kairat, University of California - Santa Barbara*

54.075-3. Culture and Tradition Across Societies (Table 3). SIG-Confucianism, Taoism, Buddhism and Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

- Culturally Adapting Simonton's Creativity Framework: Assessing Japanese Creativity through Shinto, Buddhism, and Confucianism. *Minh N. Kim, The George Washington University; Manh Tuan Kim, Vietnam National University*
- A Way of Becoming Human in the East Asian Tradition: the Educational Role of Ritualized Body. *Duck-Joo Kwak, Seoul National University*

Meaning-Generative Learning: A Mind-Based Paradigm for the AI Era, Rooted in Eastern Wisdom. *Yunfan Zuo, Central China Normal University; Yubei Chang, Central China Normal University; Qingtang Liu, Central China Normal University*

“Letting Learning Flow”: A Taoist Critique of Pedagogical Control in U.S. Elementary Bilingual Classrooms. *Yunlu Wang, Georgia State University*

‘Passive Asian Students’? A Cross-Cultural Analysis of Humility in Education. *Liz Jackson, University of Hong Kong; Emma E. Buchtel, The Education University of Hong Kong*

Chair: *Dengting Boyanton, Sino-American Educational Research Association*

Discussant: *Hongyu Wang, Oklahoma State University - Tulsa*

54.075-4. Continental Philosophy, Postmodernism, and Education (Table 4). SIG-Philosophical Studies in Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Framing Education Through Pedagogik. *Marit Honerod Hoveid, Norwegian University of Science and Technology*
Hannah Arendt and the Educator’s Responsibility. *Clifford P. Harbour, University of North Texas; Jonathon Sanders, University of North Texas; Doug Smith, Iowa State University*

Post-truth conditions and the power of the false: Embodied learning with Spinoza. *Joanna Dennis, Manchester Metropolitan University; Elizabeth De Freitas, Adelphi University*

Tension and Symbiosis of Order and Disorder in Plato’s Republic: A Dialectical Framework for Educational Thought. *Yan Huang, Peking University; Ziyue Yang, Peking University*

To make a lesson: diffracting through rhizomatic curriculum with postmethod pedagogies. *Rūta Gajauskaitė, Vilnius University*

Chair: *Raul Olmo Fregoso Bailón, University of Nevada - Reno*

54.075-5. Governing Innovation and System Change in an Era of Choice (Table 5). SIG-Charters & School Choice; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Designing the Return: Collaborative Innovation and Governance Reform in New Orleans’ School Unification. *Henderson Lewis, Louisiana State University; Veysel Altunel, Louisiana State University; Stacy-Ann Campbell, Louisiana State University; Nicholas Bijou, Einstein Charter School*

Evaluating the Alignment Between Research on School

Information and School Choice Policy Provisions. *Jason Saltmarsh, Old Dominion University; Bryan Mann, University of Kansas; Jackie Nikiema, Old Dominion University*

When Innovation Dies: Temporal Isomorphism and the Failures of Charter School Reform. *Juddson R. Taube, University of San Francisco*

Alternative Schools in the Era of School Choice: National Trends in Enrollment Over Three Decades. *Adam Kho, University of Kentucky; Nicolas Pardo, University of Southern California; Shelby Leigh Smith, University of Southern California; Sarah Rabovsky, Tennessee Department of Education*

Chair: *Jin Lee, University of Louisiana at Lafayette*

54.075-6. Critical Examination of Race, Ethnicity, Class, and Gender Roundtable: Trajectories and Outcomes, Experiences of Black and Latiné Youth (Table 6). SIG-Critical Examination of Race, Ethnicity, Class and Gender in Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

The Journey towards Lives Well Lived: Carceral Schooling and the Educational Trajectories of Chicanx Youth. *Maria C. Malagon, California State University - Fullerton*

A comparative reflection: Black children’s stories in the face of an uncertain future. *Jadyn Laixely, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Period Poverty and Menstrual Hygiene Management in Sub-Saharan African Schools: A Systematic Review. *Tarym T.C. Brown, University of Florida; Oluyemisi Oladejo, University of Florida*

Learning for Equity: Exploring the Relationship Between Ethnic-Racial Identity Projects and Youth Development in Brazil. *Julia Callegari, Northwestern University*

Chair: *Taylor C.J. Wynne, The Ohio State University*

54.075-7. Montessori Pedagogy and Practice (Table 7). SIG-Montessori Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Exploring Use of the Measure of Montessori Implementation to Understand Montessori Early Childhood Classroom Types. *Angela Murray, University of Kansas; Amelia Murray, University of Kansas; Carolyn Jean Daoust, University of Kansas; Heather E. Gerker, University of Cincinnati*

Reclaiming Montessori’s Radical Roots: Culturally Relevant Pedagogy as a Pathway to Equitable Futures. *Jazmin M Corbell, Georgia Southern University*

Integrating Computational Literacy into Montessori Pre-K Environments. *Noel Kuriakos, University of Maryland*

54.075-8. Pedagogical Models in Practice (Table 8). SIG-
Research on Learning and Instruction in Physical Education;
Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Exploring Perceived Matterings through the Lens of Adventure-based Learning. *Denis Schulz, California State University - San Marcos; Paul T. Stuhr, California State University - San Marcos*

Implementation Fidelity of the NP-UDL Intervention:

Exploring the Relationship Between Pedagogical Delivery and Student Motor Performance. *Michael Ertel, California State University Long Beach; Andrea Taliaferro, University of South Carolina; David Stodden, University of South Carolina; Pamela Beach, Rochester Institute of Technology; An De Meester, University of South Carolina; Ali S. Brian, University of South Carolina*

'It's Gonna Take Time': Enacting Culturally Relevant Physical Education in Urban Schools. *Craigory Nieman, University of South Florida - Tampa; Sara Barnard Flory, University of South Florida*

Physical Education Teachers' Experiences with Implementing TPSR Model in Lower Elementary Physical Education: A Qualitative Action Research Study. *Baofu Wang, SUNY - College at Cortland; Paul M. Wright, Northern Illinois University; Longxi Li, University of Washington; Xiaolu Liu, Georgia State University; Stacy Imagbe, Morehouse College*

Teacher Implementation Fidelity: Linking to Student Knowledge, Engagement, and Physical Activity in Concept-Based PE. *Hamid Amni, University of North Carolina - Greensboro; Jihyun Song, University of North Carolina - Greensboro; Alexander Clayton Moss, University of North Carolina - Greensboro; Alireza Hosseinikhezri, University of North Carolina - Greensboro; Chaojie Shang, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; En-Hua Chan, National Kaohsiung Normal University; Ang Chen, University of North Carolina - Greensboro*

Chair: *Mara Simon, Springfield College*

54.075-9. Science Teaching and Learning (Table 9). SIG-
Science Teaching and Learning; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Prompting Dialogic Reflection Using Peer-Partner Video Stimulated Recall in Early Elementary Science and Engineering. *Christine McGrail, University of North Dakota; Stephanie Purington, Marist College; Alicia C. Gonzales, Michigan Technological University*

STEM Instructor Perceptions of Obstacles for Implementing Racially/Ethnically Diverse Guest Speakers. *Anthony Muro Villa, University of California - Riverside; Quentin Sedlacek, Southern Methodist University; Michelle Friend, University*

of Nebraska - Omaha; Sara Dozier, California State University - Long Beach; Karla Lomeli, Santa Clara University; Greses Perez, Tufts University; Joel Alejandro Mejia, University of Cincinnati

How Role Models Work: Tackling Socio-cultural Challenges to Empower Youth for Female Participation in Science. *Yu-Hui Chang, National Sun Yat-sen University; Yueh-Chang Li, National Sun Yat-sen University; Shih-An Yang, National Sun Yat-sen University; I-Shin Liu, National Sun Yat-sen University/Institute of Education*

Chair: *Weiyi Ding, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

54.075-10. Dual Enrollment & Educators (Table 10). Division J
- Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Dual-Credit Gatekeepers: The Relationship Between Educator Beliefs & Student Participation in Dual-Credit Offerings. *Kimberly Pack-Cosme, University of Texas at Austin; Matthew S. Giani, University of Texas at Austin; Rashi Agarwal, University of Texas at Austin; Madison E. Andrews, University of Texas at Austin; Kait Ogden, University of Texas at Austin*

Dual Enrollment: A Pipeline to the Host Institution and Careers in Teaching. *Kelly M. McGinn, Temple University; Samantha N. Kimmel, Temple University; Juliet D. Curci, Temple University*

54.076. AERA Roundtable Session Friday 11:45 am - Gold 4;
Roundtable Session

54.076-1. Nested Realities: School, Society, and Transformation in Education (Table 1). Division C -
Learning and Instruction; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Contextualizing Self-Efficacy: How Bilingualism, Family SES, and School Environment Shape Mathematics Beliefs in U.S. 4th Graders. *Yuhwa Hong, University of Massachusetts - Amherst*

A Multilevel Analysis of Socioeconomic Status Disparities: The Role of School Context in Shaping Student Outcomes. *Pooja Roy, University of Houston; Nobonita Saha, University of Houston; Tamal Joyti Roy, University of Houston; Nelson W Chavez Cubas, University of Houston; Rhonda Schere, University of Houston; Norma Olvera*

Multilevel Analysis of the Relationship between School Community Member Relationships and Students' Cognitive Competencies : A Comparative Study of Korea and the United States. *Jiyoung Kang, Seoul National University; Moonyoung Eom, Seoul National University*

Failure to Learn: Intra-Disciplinarity as a Process. *Jonathan*

Desmon Russell Pérez, The School of The New York Times; Quennie Dong, University of California - Berkeley; Shreya Kailey Sheel, University of California - Berkeley
HistoFuturity As a Metatheory of Educational Change. *Samuela Mouzaour, Michigan State University*

Chair: *Kimiko Ching, The Ohio State University*

54.076-2. Self-Regulation and Emotional Development in the age of AI (Table 2). SIG-Advanced Technologies for Learning; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Beyond Prompting: Empowering Student Self-Regulation in Generative AI Writing Through a Learning Analytics Dashboard. *Angxuan Chen, Peking University*
Comparing the Effects of Technology-Based Psychoeducation on Emotion Regulation Skills and Mindfulness. *Sümeyye Eliz Burhan Karacan, Istanbul Aydin University*
Designing and Evaluating Collaborative Scaffolding in Immersive VR Collaborative Learning within the Metaverse. *Chi-Han Lee, National Tsing Hua University; Cheng-Huan Chen, National Tsing Hua University*
Empowering Children's Dialogic Reading with a Bilingual LLM-Powered Conversational Agent: A Design Probe Study. *Feiwen Xiao, University of Pennsylvania; Jiaju Lin, Pennsylvania State University; Zhaohui Li, Pennsylvania State University; Xiaohan Zou, Pennsylvania State University; Chih-Yi Chen, Pennsylvania State University; Dandan Yang, University of California - Los Angeles; Wenting Zou, Pennsylvania State University; Jinjun Xiong, University at Buffalo - SUNY*
Unpacking GenAI Literacy: The Role of Individual Drivers and Engagement Levels. *Mohammadreza Farrokhnia, University of Twente; Leonie Fischer, The University of Twente; Ghasem Salimi, Shiraz University - Iran; Seyyed Kazem Banihashem, Open Universiteit Nederland; Omid Noroozi, Wageningen University and Research*

54.076-3. Artificial Intelligence and Learner-Centered Educational Innovation (Table 3). SIG-Computer and Internet Application in Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Computer Science Teacher Perspectives on the Impact of AI Advancements in K-12 Education. *Sonia Koshy, Kapor Foundation; Bryan Twarek, Computer Science Teachers Association; Laura Hinton, Stanford University*
Faculty perceptions on the use of AI at HBCUs. *Walter A. Brown, Jackson State University; amy c davis, Jackson State University*
Integrating Artificial Intelligence into Morality Education: Validating an Instructional Design Model for Secondary

Classrooms. *Gaeun Park, Seoul National University; Dohee Han, Seoul National University; Xuantong Guo, Seoul National University; Yeahjune Han, Seoul National University; Eunseo Lee, Seoul National University; Sumin Hong, Seoul National University; Jesse Ha, Montclair State University*

Positionings of GenAI in the feedback process and its efficacy in argumentative essay writing. *Chun Lai, The University of Hong Kong; mengru pan, The University of Hong Kong*
Measuring teachers' generative AI use: Scale Development and Validation. *Fangzhou Jin, The University of Hong Kong; Hongyun DENG, University of Hong Kong; Zhengyu Yang, University of Hong Kong; Zhong Sun, Capital Normal University; Chin-Hsi Lin, University of Hong Kong*

54.076-4. Communities, Care, and Co-Design for Inclusive Learning (Table 4). SIG-Design and Technology; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

A Four-Year Longitudinal Analysis of Community of Inquiry in an Interactive Synchronous HyFlex Course. *Lakshmy Mohandas, Purdue University; Adrie A. Koehler, Purdue University; Nathan Mentzer, Purdue University*
Designing AI for Social Good: Critical AI Literacy in a Culturally Grounded Youth Curriculum. *Hyejeong Lee, University of Texas - San Antonio; Suraj Bandela, University of Texas - San Antonio; James Hernandez, Harlandale ISD; Tiffany Emanuel, University of Texas - San Antonio*
Understanding Modern Slavery Using Human-Centered Design in a Collaborative Online International Learning Experience. *Joey Shepherd, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Saadeddine S. Shehab, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Chair: *Shenghua Zha, University of South Alabama*

54.076-5. Future Directions for Faculty Development in Health Professions and Biomedical Education Abstract (Table 5). Division I - Education in the Professions; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Constructing New Educational Futures: Integrating AI and Instructional Design in Faculty Development for Clinical Educators. *Ramona Dorough, UT Southwestern Medical Center; Yulia Piller, UT Southwestern Medical Center*
Factors Affecting Clinical Instructor Participation in Faculty Development Across Workplace Settings: A Scoping Review. *Erin Green, California State University - Sacramento; Bridget Colleen O'Brien, University of California - San Francisco; Manon Kluijtmans, Utrecht University; Huiju Carrie Chen, Kaiser Permanente Bernard*

J. Tyson School of Medicine

Focusing on the Whole Person: Flourishing in Faculty Development. *Abbey Bachmann, The University of Texas - Health Science Center at Houston*

Future Directions in Faculty Development in Health Professions and Biomedical Education Research: Building Infrastructures for Interdisciplinary Collaboration. *Ashley E. Grantham, University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill; Yuane Jia, Rutgers University; Rebekah L. Layton, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*

Chair: *Ashley E. Grantham, University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill*

Discussant: *Anita Samuel, Uniformed Services University of the Health Sciences*

54.076-6. Cognitive Processes and Learning Pathways: Innovative Approaches to Assessment and Development (Table 6). SIG-Cognition and Assessment; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Challenging Conventional Approaches: An Expert System Model for Evaluating Open-Ended Assessment Items. *Bengi Birgili Karabulut, MEF University*

From Poverty to Risk: Cognitive Roots of Tobacco Use Through Executive Function. *Qijia Wang, University of Cambridge*

The Effect of Motor Sequence on Written Word Production of a New Script Moderated by Script Experience and Visual Complexity. *Xianglin Zhang, University of Maryland; Min Wang, University of Maryland; Yi Dai, University of Maryland*

Tracing Epistemic Growth in Scientific Inquiry: A Longitudinal Study of Cognitive and Structural Development. *Mustafa CAKIR, Marmara University; Anil Yurdakul, Marmara University; Ozgur Kivilcan Dogan, Marmara University*

54.076-7. Reconceptualizing Measurement, Classification, and Validity in Critical Quantitative Work (Table 7). SIG-Critical Quantitative Methodologies; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Critical Construct Validation of the Perspectives on Play-Based Pedagogy Scale: Early Childhood Workers as Experts. *Phoebe Gilpin, Hunter College - CUNY*

Deconstructing Dualities: An International Student Index as a Critical Alternative to Binary Classifications. *Yun-Han Weng, The Ohio State University; Anisha Gill-Morris, The Ohio State University; Matthew J. Mayhew, The Ohio State University*

Illuminating Contradictions: Racialized Aberrations and the Non-hierarchical Limits of Quantification. *Nathaniel D.*

Stewart, University of Minnesota

Student Perceptions as Structural Indicators of Stratified Postsecondary Access. *Catherina Villafuerte, University of Connecticut*

Unveiling Racism: A Systematic Review of Racism Survey Measures in Education. *Juan R. Cruz, Harvard University; Brein Mosely, Harvard University; Wendy Castillo, Montclair State University; Rachel L. Renbarger, FHI 360; Sasha C. Mejia-Bradford, University of Pennsylvania*

Chair: *Hyeri Hong, California State University - Fresno*

54.076-8. Language Assessment for Students with Disabilities (Table 8). SIG-Inclusion and Accessibility in Educational Assessment; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Assessability of Kindergarten English Language Proficiency Assessments for Students with Low Vision: Considerations from Educators. *Anna Rhoad-Drogalis, Wisconsin Center for Education Research; Laurene L. Christensen, Wisconsin Center for Education Research; Kristen Burton, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Melinda Rossi, University of Colorado - Denver*

Impact of ESSA on Alternate Assessment Access for English Learners with Significant Cognitive Disabilities. *Nami Shin, University of Kansas; Meagan Karvonen, University of Kansas; Melissa L. Gholson, University of Kansas*

Proficiency Outcomes of English Learners with Significant Cognitive Disabilities Before, During, and After the Pandemic. *Glenn A. Poole, WIDA; Narék Sahakyan, WIDA*
Voices from Educators: Decision-Making on Accommodations for WIDA ACCESS. *I-Chun Hsiao, University of Iowa; Anna Rhoad-Drogalis, Wisconsin Center for Education Research; Laurene L. Christensen, Wisconsin Center for Education Research*

Chair: *Sara E. Witmer, Michigan State University*

54.076-9. Teaching Research Methods to Diverse Learners (Table 9). SIG-Teaching and Learning Research Methods; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Moving Past the Research Paper: Centering Metaliteracy in Effective Research Assignment Design. *Matthew Weirick Johnson, University of South Florida; Jennifer Slagus, Brock University*

Teaching Group-Level Assessment: Learnings from an Explanatory Sequential Mixed Methods Study. *Heather E. Gerker, University of Cincinnati; Miriam B. Raider-Roth, University of Cincinnati; Mindy Gold, Gold Learning Solutions*

A Project-Based Approach to a Master's-level Educational

Research Class. *Karen Moran Jackson, Soka University of America; Dana Stewart, California State University - Bakersfield*

I Don't Belong Here: Communities of Caring and Vulnerability Through Narrative Analysis. *Shelly Melchior, University of West Alabama; Hazel Nichol Foster, Tuscaloosa City School; Lisa Heard, University of West Alabama; Anthony Brock, Valiant Cross Academy; Felissa Clemons, Valiant Cross Academy*

Chair: *Lori A. Foote, University of Cincinnati*

54.076-10. AI-Enhanced Problem Solving and Instructional Design Frameworks (Table 10). Division C - Learning and Instruction; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

A Descriptive Model of AI-Assisted Information Problem-Solving (AI-IPS): Core Competencies, Opportunities, and Challenges in Higher Education. *Xinyan Zhou, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; SHUHENG SHI, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Thomas K.F. Chiu, The Chinese University of Hong Kong*

Beneath Student-AI Use: Motivational Profiles Of Student Engagement With Generative AI. *Muhammad Amir Fuseig, University of Maryland; Patricia A. Alexander, University of Maryland*

Designing with CARE: A Human-AI Framework for Inclusive Faculty Development in Non-English Contexts. *Aigerim Shilibekova, Simon Fraser University*

Factors Predicting College Student AI Use for Academic Tasks. *Moon-Heum Cho, Syracuse University; EunHae Grace Park, Ball State University; Seongmi Lim, Ball State University; Hyeonho Henry Yu, Ball State University*

The Efficacy of Using Generative AI to Render Illustrative Diagrams to Accompany Mathematics Word Problems. *Candace A. Walkington, Southern Methodist University; Theodora Beauchamp, Southern Methodist University; Jiabao Wen, Southern Methodist University; Jonathan Isaac, Southern Methodist University; Robert DiBiano, Ailectric*

Chair: *Chaewon Kim, Florida State University*

Division and SIG Posters

54.077. AERA Poster Session Friday 11:45am; Poster Session

54.077-1. AERA Promising Scholarship in Education

Research: Dissertation Fellows and Their Research Poster Session. AERA Promising Scholarship in Education Research: Dissertation Fellows and Their Research; Invited Poster Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Posters:

1. Examining Pre-K Effectiveness by Alternative Childcare Options: Evidence from the Tennessee Voluntary Pre-K Study (Poster 1). *Johanna Bernard, University of Pennsylvania*
2. Neighborhoods and Educational Opportunities: An Examination of Factors Affecting Sense of Belonging in High School (Poster 2). *Naomi Sara Duran, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*
3. Reading Rights: Black Americans and the Constitutional Case for Literacy (Poster 3). *Vania Blaiklock, College of William & Mary*
4. Cross-border temporalities: Learning with and across borders in transfronterizx youths' schooling (Poster 4). *Isaac Alejandro Felix, University of California - Berkeley*
5. The Black Student Parent Experience: An Exploration of Institutional Practices of Student Parent Servingness (Poster 5). *Alexus SA Laster, Howard University*
6. Abolition Dissonance: How Carcerality in Schools Persists in the Anti-Carceral Movement (Poster 6). *Pharren Miller, University of California - Los Angeles*
7. The Children's Interpersonal Mattering at School Scale: A Psychometric Exploration (Poster 7). *Camila Polanco, University of Delaware*
8. Future Indigenous Scientists: Tribal-University Partnerships for Building Amah Mutsun Science Curriculum (Poster 8). *Carolyn T. Rodriguez, University of California - Los Angeles*
9. Understanding Historically Black Colleges and Universities (HBCUs) through Identity, Finance, and Community Impact (Poster 9). *Tre Wells, Northwestern University*
10. Amid an Anti-Black Schooling Landscape: Racialized Risk Assessments in Black Families' School Choice (Poster 10). *De'Ja Wood, Vanderbilt University*
11. Teaching Logic for Social Justice: How Students' Reasoning About Axioms and Definitions Can Support Their Reasoning Around Prisons and Abolition (Poster 11). *Megumi Asada, Rutgers University*
12. Teacher Housing Initiatives: An Embedded Case Study of Race, Place, and the School-Housing Nexus (Poster 12). *Jackquelin Bristol, University of Colorado - Boulder*
13. Trade-offs, Barriers, and Contradictions: California Early Childhood Educators' Experiences During Universal PreKindergarten Implementation (Poster 13). *Micah Card, University of California - Santa Cruz*
14. Violent Crimes, Classroom Quality, and Child Development: Effects of Community Violence on Education Outcomes (Poster 14). *Juan Camilo Cristancho, University of California - Irvine*
15. Envisioning Beyond Community - Community Organizing and Education Planning Across Neighborhoods (Poster 15). *Andrew Frangos, University of Chicago*
16. Exploring the Dynamics of a Culturally Sensitive School-Based Social-Emotional Learning Program for Rural Chinese Children: Evaluating Effectiveness, Mediators, and Moderators (Poster 16). *Linyun Fu, University of Chicago*

17. Mapping the Mechanisms of Interdisciplinary Learning Transfer from Reading to Math Achievement: Evidence from a Large-Scale Randomized Controlled Trial (Poster 17). *Joshua Baer Gilbert, Harvard University; James S. Kim, Harvard University*
18. Reimagining Safety for Black Queer Students: Embracing Intersectionality and the Complexity of Black Queer Existence (Poster 18). *LaShanda Harbin, University of Wisconsin - Madison*
19. Rooted: The Influences of Ancestral Archives with Black and Latina Femmes (Poster 19). *Alexis E. Hunter, University of Colorado - Boulder*
20. Toward Literacies of Transnational Racialization: Recently Arrived Immigrant Youth Reading the World (Poster 20). *Rita Kamani-Renedo, Stanford University*
21. The Secondary Diaspora: Black Women in NCAA Division I Basketball (Poster 21). *Iman Lathan, University at Buffalo - SUNY*
22. Beyond Systems Thinking: Political Literacy, Adaptive Capacity, and Biocultural Knowledge in Post-Wildfire Environmental Education (Poster 22). *Jadda M. Miller, University of California - Davis*
23. Modern Missionaries and the Rise of Indigenous Education in Mexico. Reinventing Catholicism in the Post-Revolutionary Secular School (Poster 23). *Marino Miranda Noriega, University of Wisconsin - Madison*
24. Heritage in the Making: How Black Elite Parents Negotiate Cultural Transmission (Poster 24). *Chinyere Odim, Brown University*
25. Latinx Youth as AI Designers: Building Their Communities' Present and Future (Poster 25). *Santiago Ojeda-Ramirez, University of California - Irvine*
26. Transmodality in Translingual Practice: Teaching and Learning Through Sound, Language, and Body in Fandango Workshops (Poster 26). *Yared Portillo, University of California - Berkeley*
27. Challenging Racialized Burdens: Financial Aid Experiences of First-Generation, Low-Income Latinx Students in California (Poster 27). *Jaime Ramirez-Mendoza, University of California - Davis*
28. Restorying the Cape Fear Watershed through Black Ecologies (Poster 28). *Maya Revell, University of Oregon*
29. Repurposing Technologies as Digital Pedagogy Design Work in Oaxaca, Mexico (Poster 29). *Emanuel Suarez Jimenez, University of California - Santa Cruz*
30. Agrarian Village Schools, Rural Rebellion, and the Financing of Underdevelopment in the French Empire (Poster 30). *Austin Vo, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*
31. Revising Roles, Transforming Trajectories?: Exploring Community College Baccalaureate Programs and Educational Access, Success, and Equity. *Davis Vo, University of California - Los Angeles*
32. Becoming the "Mystical Unicorn": Understanding the Racialized Illegality Experiences of Undocumented Asian College Students in California (Poster 31). *Siyue Lena Wang, University of California - Los Angeles*
33. Beyond Exclusion: A Historical Examination of Chinese International Student Protests During the Chinese Exclusion Era (1882-1943) (Poster 32). *Yu Wang, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*
34. November 20th as Pedagogy: How AfroBrazilians utilized Celebration to Retell their History (Poster 33). *Jasmine Norma Watson, Pennsylvania State University*
35. Southern Academies: The Proliferation of All-White Private Schools after Brown and Their Legacy for Students (Poster 34). *Danielle Williamson, Boston University*
- Chair: *George L. Wimberly, American Educational Research Association*
- 54.077-2. Individual and Institutional Anti-Racism at a Predominantly White Independent School.** Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Poster Session Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 11:45am to 1:15pm
- Poster:
36. Individual and Institutional Anti-Racism at a Predominantly White Independent School (Poster 35). *Nerisa Arias, Fordham University; Clarence Ball, Fordham University; Dorcas Boateng Asa-Ntow, Fordham University; Jane Bolgatz, Fordham University; Graham Johnson, Fordham University; Jazlyn Mary Mena, Fordham University; Lindsay Rosoff, Fordham University; Shanna Silien, Fordham University*
- 54.077-3. Naming Our Priorities: Centering Justice and Anti-Racism in Teacher Education Curriculum.** Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Poster Session Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 11:45am to 1:15pm
- Poster:
37. Naming Our Priorities: Centering Justice and Anti-Racism in Teacher Education Curriculum (Poster 36). *Vanessa Nizeyimana Louis, University of Michigan; Debi Khasnabis, University of Michigan; Meri Tenney Muirhead, University of Michigan; Maren Elyse Oberman, University of Michigan*
- 54.077-4. Reflexive Praxis and Transnational Habitus: Narratives of Identity, Transformation, and Ideological Clarity in Teacher Education.** Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Poster Session Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 11:45am to 1:15pm
- Poster:
38. Reflexive Praxis and Transnational Habitus: Narratives of Identity, Transformation, and Ideological Clarity in Teacher Education (Poster 37). *Lei Jiang, University of Kansas; Shuzhan Li, Ithaca College; Wenyang Sun, University of Utah*

54.077-5. The Affective Life of Whiteness: Researcher Reflections on Professional Learning Interactions.

Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Poster Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Poster:

39. The Affective Life of Whiteness: Researcher Reflections on Professional Learning Interactions (Poster 38). *Elizabeth Metts, Vanderbilt University; Karen Underwood, Vanderbilt University*

54.077-6. AERA Division K Section 6 In-Service Educators - Poster Session 3. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Poster Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Posters:

40. Creating Space for EFL Teachers' Engagement with AI: A Nudge-Based Experimental Study (Poster 39). *Jiani Rong, East China Normal University; Shuangye Chen, East China Normal University*
41. Cultivating Hope through Professional Learning Communities in Rural Elementary Schools (Poster 40). *Nien-ching Michelle Chuang, National Pingtung University; Yating Lee, National Pingtung University; Yi-Ku Ting, University of Taipei; Su-Ching Lai, University of Taipei*
42. Enhancing Teacher Professional Development through Knowledge Building and Generative AI-Based Assessment for STEM Lesson Design (Poster 41). *Cing-Sin Lin, National Chengchi University; Guo-Tsai Hung, National Taichung University of Science and Technology; Chih-Hsuan Chang, National Kaohsiung University of Science and Technology; Mei-Ju Chen, National Tsing Hua University; Huang Yao Hong, National Chengchi University*
43. Fostering Positive Emotions: The Impact of Teacher's Extrinsic Emotion Regulation on Student Learning (Poster 42). *Yanan Xu, Xi'an Jiao Tong Liverpool University; Qian Wang, Xi'an Jiaotong-Liverpool University; Haibo Gu, Soochow University*
44. How do teacher emotions affect teaching approaches? The mediating role of aspiration and depersonalization (Poster 43). *Jing Wang, Zhejiang University; Shufei Xiong, 浙江大学*
45. Invention and Revision: Our DBR Journey in Iteratively Designing Professional Development for College Composition Instructors (Poster 44). *Carrie L. James, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Weronika Kaczmarczyk-Smith, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*
46. "Like a Family Reunion": Cultivating Bonding, Bridging, and Instrumental Ties Among Math Educators of Color (Poster 45). *Fenot Aklog, Bank Street College of Education;*

Yeonji Kang, Bank Street College of Education; Hanna Nichols, Bank Street College of Education; Paula Lee Poy, Bank Street College of Education; Tarima Levine, Bank Street College of Education

47. Making an Impact in Teacher Education for Sustainable Development through an In-service Professional Development Program (Poster 46). *Mustafa Öztürk, Boğaziçi University*
48. Taking the Parent Perspective in Teachers' Professional Development Discourse in the Bedouin Society (Poster 47). *Hadeel Omar Edrees Dabbah, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev; Dana Vedder-Weiss, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev; Idit Fast, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev; Haled Sayed, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev*
49. Teacher Professional Learning to Support Multilingual Learners in Engineering Education (Poster 48). *Meghan Macias, WestEd; Ashley Iveland, WestEd; Ruchita Patel, WestEd*
50. Teachers' perceptions of professional learning and the associated factors 1-5 years after participation (Poster 49). *Olivia J Bruner, Arizona State University; Kiley Pooler, Arizona State University; Karen A. Koellner, Arizona State University; Nanette M. Seago, WestEd; Nicora Placa, Hunter College - CUNY; Sarah Warner, WestEd*
51. The Construction of Infant/toddler Teachers' Professional Learning Community in the Chinese Context: Dilemmas and Strategies (Poster 50). *Dejin He, East China Normal University*
52. The Virginia New Teacher Support Program (Poster 51). *Mary Beth Cancienne, James Madison University*
53. Transforming Teachers' Ideology and Practice towards Multilingual Learners: Knowing My Students is Knowing Myself (Poster 52). *Annette M. Daoud, California State University - San Marcos; Ana M. Hernandez, California State University - San Marcos; Elsie Solis, California State University - San Marcos; Alma Sanchez, California State University - San Marcos*
54. PLCs' Contribution to Homeroom Teachers' Coping and Resilience During Wartime. (Poster 53). *Michal Hanouka, Tel Aviv University; Hila Vaizman Ben David, Hemdat HaDorom College of Education; Stav Ziv, Tel Aviv University; Sharon Wasserman, Atchalta (Professional Development Program for Educators)*

54.078. Meet the Editors - Journal Talks Session 5. AERA Sessions; Journal Talks

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

1. Canadian Journal of Science, Mathematics and Technology Education (Table 1). *Douglas E. McDougall, University of Toronto - OISE*
2. Journal of Research in Childhood Education (Table 2). *Anne Bauer, Childhood Education International; Chenyi Zhang,*

- Georgia State University; Hani Morgan, University of Southern Mississippi; Minyi LI, Beijing Normal University; Lena Lee, Miami University (OH); Samara Madrid Akpovo, University of Tennessee; John Kambutu, University of Wyoming; Wing Kai Fung, Liverpool Hope University; Laurent Ndiujye, United Arab Emirates University
3. Mentoring and Tutoring: Partnership in Learning (Table 3). M. Nathan R. Templeton, East Texas A&M University; Beverly J. Irby, Texas A&M University; Nahed Abdelrahman, The University of Southern Mississippi; Hamada Elfarargy, South Dakota State University
4. Racial Justice in Multilingual Education (Table 4). María Cioe-Pena, University of Pennsylvania; Kara Mitchell Viesca, University of Nebraska - Lincoln; Chris K. Chang-Bacon, University of Virginia; Aris M. Clemons, University of Tennessee; Claudia Rodriguez-Mojica, University of California - Davis; Kate Seltzer, Rowan University; Manka M. Varghese, University of Washington; Diana Lalata, University of Pennsylvania
5. International Journal of Leadership in Education (Table 5). Álvaro González, Universidad Católica Silva Henríquez; Duncan Waite, Texas State University; Robert E. White, Saint Francis Xavier University; Victoria Showunmi, University College London - IOE; Elson S.Y. Szeto, The Education University of Hong Kong; Livia A.J. Jesacher-Roessler, Friedrich-Alexander-University Erlangen-Nuremberg; Koksai Banoglu, The Education University of Hong Kong; Pinyan Lin, Beijing Normal University; Munube Yilmaz, Texas State University; José Manuel Améstica Abarca, Diego Portales University
6. Journal of Advanced Academics (Table 6). Angela Novak, East Carolina University; Keishana L. Barnes, University of Memphis; Hernan Castillo-Hermosilla, Purdue University; Alejandra Amaris Fernández Morgado, Florida International University; Celeste DC Sodergren, University of Connecticut; Yuyang Shen, University of North Texas; Vicky Weiqing Ji, University of North Texas
7. Journal of First-generation Student Success (Table 7). Kem Saichaie, University of California, Los Angeles; Jason K. Wallace, Mississippi State University
8. Journal of Geoscience Education (Table 8). Kathryn M. Bateman, Pennsylvania State University - Harrisburg
9. European Journal of Teacher Education (Table 9). Manuela Heinz, University of Galway
10. Frontiers in Education (Table 10). Margaret Grogan, Chapman University; Liz Malnar, Frontiers Media
11. International Journal of Education Through Art (Table 11). Ahran Koo, California State University - Fresno
12. Journal of Educational Foundations (JEF) (Table 12). Kendall Dwayne Deas, University of South Carolina
13. Diaspora, Indigenous, and Minority Education: Studies of Migration, Integration, Equity, and Cultural Survival (DIME) (Table 13). Bruce Anthony Collet, Bowling Green State University
14. British Journal of Educational Technology (BJET) (Table 14). Louis Major, University of Manchester
15. Journal of Engineering Education (Table 15). Joyce Main, Purdue University; James L Huff, University of Georgia
16. Urban Education (Table 16). Rich Milner, Vanderbilt University
17. Review of Educational Research (Table 17). Daniel D. Liou, Arizona State University; Angela M. Labistre Champion, Pennsylvania State University
18. Educational Researcher (Table 18). Anjalé D. Welton, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Brian An, University of Iowa
- 54.079. e-Lightning Ed-Talk Session 12 - Stage 1.** AERA e-Lightning Ed-Talks; AERA Ed Talk
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Exhibit Hall A - Stage 1; 11:45am to 1:15pm
- Participants:
Teacher Professional Learning to Support Multilingual Learners in Engineering Education (Stage 1, 11:50 AM). Meghan Macias, WestEd; Ashley Iveland, WestEd; Ruchita Patel, WestEd
Taking the Parent Perspective in Teachers' Professional Development Discourse in the Bedouin Society (Stage 1, 11:59 AM). Hadeel Omar Edrees Dabbah, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev; Dana Vedder-Weiss, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev; Idit Fast, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev; Haled Sayed, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev
"Like a Family Reunion": Cultivating Bonding, Bridging, and Instrumental Ties Among Math Educators of Color (Stage 1, 12:08 PM). Fenot Aklog, Bank Street College of Education; Yeonji Kang, Bank Street College of Education; Hanna Nichols, Bank Street College of Education; Paula Lee Poy, Bank Street College of Education; Tarima Levine, Bank Street College of Education
Fostering Positive Emotions: The Impact of Teacher's Extrinsic Emotion Regulation on Student Learning (Stage 1, 12:17 PM). Yanan Xu, Xi'an Jiao Tong Liverpool University; Qian Wang, Xi'an Jiaotong-Liverpool University; Haibo Gu, Soochow University
PLCs' Contribution to Homeroom Teachers' Coping and Resilience During Wartime. (Stage 1, 12:26 PM). michal hanouka, Tel Aviv University; Hila Vaitzman Ben David, Hemdat HaDarom College of Education; Stav Ziv, Tel Aviv University; Sharon Wasserman, Atchalta (Professional Development Program for Educators)
- Chair: Robert Pianta, University of Virginia
- 54.080. Promising Scholarship in Education Research Ed-Talk (Stage 2).** AERA e-Lightning Ed-Talks; AERA Ed Talk
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Exhibit Hall A - Stage 2; 11:45am to 1:15pm
- Participants:
The Black Student Parent Experience: An Exploration of

Institutional Practices of Student Parent Servingness (Stage 2, 11:50 AM). *Alexus SA Laster, Howard University*

Future Indigenous Scientists: Tribal-University Partnerships for Building Amah Mutsun Science Curriculum (Stage 2, 11:59 AM). *Carolyn T. Rodriguez, University of California - Los Angeles*

Amid an Anti-Black Schooling Landscape: Racialized Risk Assessments in Black Families' School Choice (Stage 2, 12:08 PM). *De'Ja Wood, Vanderbilt University*

Reading Rights: Black Americans and the Constitutional Case for Literacy (Stage 2, 12:17 PM). *Vania Blaiklock, College of William & Mary*

Trade-offs, Barriers, and Contradictions: California Early Childhood Educators' Experiences During Universal PreKindergarten Implementation (Stage 2, 12:26 PM). *Micah Card, University of California - Santa Cruz*

54.081. Promising Scholarship in Education Research Ed-Talk (Stage 3). AERA e-Lightning Ed-Talks; AERA Ed Talk Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Exhibit Hall A - Stage 3; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

The Secondary Diaspora: Black Women in NCAA Division I Basketball (Stage 3, 11:50 AM). *Iman Lathan, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

Envisioning Beyond Community - Community Organizing and Education Planning Across Neighborhoods (Stage 3, 11:59 AM). *Andrew Frangos, University of Chicago*

Latinx Youth as AI Designers: Building Their Communities' Present and Future (Stage 3, 12:08 PM). *Santiago Ojeda-Ramirez, University of California - Irvine*

Becoming the "Mystical Unicorn": Understanding the Racialized Illegality Experiences of Undocumented Asian College Students in California (Stage 3, 12:17 PM). *Siyue Lena Wang, University of California - Los Angeles*

The Children's Interpersonal Mattering at School Scale: A Psychometric Exploration (Stage 3, 12:26PM). *Camila Polanco, University of Delaware*

Friday, April 10th, 12:00 pm

55.010. Educators as Upstanders: Building Allyship to Combat Antisemitism in Schools and on Campuses, George Washington University. Affiliated Groups; Panel Discussion
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, San Gabriel C; 12:00-1:30pm

Friday, April 10th, 12:45 pm

Professional Development Courses

56.010. PD26-13 Doing Surveys & Research with the RAND Survey Panels. Professional Development and Training Committee; Professional Development Course
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Plaza I; 12:45-4:45pm
Directors: *Julia Heath Kaufman, RAND Corporation; Sy Doan, RAND Corporation*
Instructors: *Elizabeth D. Steiner, RAND Corporation; Erin Daniels, MGT; Jaleh Shambayati, MGT*

56.011. PD26-14 Advanced Meta-Analysis. Professional Development and Training Committee; Professional Development Course
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Plaza II; 12:45-4:45pm
Director: *Terri D. Pigott, Georgia State University*
Instructor: *Ryan Williams, American Institutes for Research*

Friday, April 10th, 1:45 pm

Governance Meetings and Events

57.001. American Educational Research Journal: Closed Editors' Meeting. AERA Governance; Governance Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 513; 1:45-3:15pm
Chair: *Motoko Akiba, Florida State University*

57.002. Review of Educational Research: Closed Editorial Board Meeting. AERA Governance; Governance Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 518; 1:45-3:15pm
Chair: *John Neikirk, American Educational Research Association*

AERA Related Activities

57.010. Things We Imagined: The Film. AERA Related Activities; Invited Speaker Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 411 (Theatre); 1:45-3:15pm
Chair: *Candace N. Hall, Southern Illinois University - Edwardsville*

Presidential Sessions

57.011. Bridging Histories and New Horizons: Interorganizational Leadership for Equitable Educational Futures. AERA Presidential Session; Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 408A;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants: *Tabbye M. Chavous, American Educational Research Association; Felice J. Levine, AERA Emerita; Geovana Mendonça Lunardi Mendes, Universidade do Estado de Santa Catarina*

Facilitator: *Rich Milner, Vanderbilt University*

57.012. Historicizing Los Angeles: Envisioning New Educational Futures in Latinx Radical Imaginations. AERA Presidential Session Cosponsored with Spotlight on Los Angeles and the Region; Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 403A;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Recovering Early Histories of LA Latinx Teachers. *Laura K. Munoz, University of Nebraska - Lincoln*

Reimagining ability differences through a proleptic epistemic culture. *Alfredo J. Artiles, Stanford University*

Organizational responses to state-sanctioned violence. *Gina Ann Garcia, University of California - Berkeley*

Where Diasporas Meet: AfroLatinx Educational Design in LA's Shifting Landscape. *Krista L. Cortes, University of Pennsylvania*

The polyrhythmic skin of Echo Park Lake, Los Angeles: Brujeros and rumberos teaching solidarity. *Amalia Z. Dache, University of Pennsylvania*

Holding Complexity, Weaving New Worlds: How Latinx Epistemologies Transform Convivencia and Solidarity. *Cecilia Rios-Aguilar, University of California - Los Angeles*

Convivencia to guide new futures in computing education: Bringing opportunities to Los Angeles. *Anne-Marie Nunez, University of Texas - El Paso*

Leveraging Critical Latinx Indigeneities (CLI) as an Analytic in Mapping Compounded Hegemonies in Multiple and Overlapping Settler Colonial Contexts. *Luis Urrieta, University of Texas at Austin*

Silence, Swagger, and Sound: Jotería Listening as a Method of Unforgetting. *Omi Salas-SantaCruz, University of Utah*

Faithful Witnessing, Convivencia, and Solidarity in Los Angeles. *Dolores Delgado Bernal, Loyola Marymount University; William Perez, Loyola Marymount University*

Youth Work is Sacred Work: Faithful Witnessing and Hanging Out in the City of the Angels. *Cindy Cruz, University of Arizona*

Chair: *Kris D. Gutiérrez, University of California - Berkeley*

57.013. Honoring Youth Mental Health through Abolitionist Education: K-12 Students Researching Radically Healing Futures. AERA Presidential Session; Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 408B;
1:45-3:15pm

Chair: *Yolanda Sealey-Ruiz, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Participants: *Patrick Camangian, University of San Francisco; Joy Diaz-Noriega, Downer Elementary School; Seth Duncan, University of California - Los Angeles; Tiera C. Tanksley, University of Colorado - Boulder; Keara L. Williams, University of California - Los Angeles*

Discussants: *Yolanda Sealey-Ruiz, Teachers College, Columbia University; Bettina L. Love, Teachers College, Columbia University*

57.014. Indigenous Education Across Tovaangar: Past, Present, Trans-Indigenous, and Future Horizons. AERA Presidential Session Cosponsored with Spotlight on Los Angeles and the Region; Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 406AB;
1:45-3:15pm

Chair: *Ananda M. Marin, University of California - Los Angeles*

Panelists: *Theresa J. Stewart-Ambo, University of California - Los Angeles; Kelly Leah Stewart, University of California, Los Angeles; Kēhaulani Vaughn, University of California - Riverside; Charles Sepulveda, The University of Utah*

57.015. Sankofa Pedagogies: Designing and Implementing Reparative Black Studies Curricula. AERA Presidential Session; Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 404AB;
1:45-3:15pm

Chairs: *Tolani Britton, University of California - Berkeley; Hilary E. Walker, University of California - Berkeley*

Panelists: *Sonya Douglass, Teachers College, Columbia University; Latosha Guy, King Drew Magnet School; Michael Hines, Stanford University; Shaunté Yvette Hill, Santa Clara University; Joyce E. King, Georgia State University; Jeremy Martin, University of California - Berkeley; Jacquelyn Ollison, University of the Pacific; Mauro Sifuentes, University of San Francisco; Hilary E. Walker, University of California - Berkeley; Honey Walrond, University of California - Berkeley*

Honorary President Edmund W. Gordon Series

57.016. Emancipatory Artificial Intelligence: Unforgetting AI

Histories to Reimagine Liberatory Futures. AERA Honorary President Edmund W. Gordon Series; Symposium Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 403B; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Emancipatory Artificial Intelligence: Unforgetting AI Histories to Reimagine Liberatory Futures. *Thema Monroe-White, George Mason University*

Technology Innovates to Incarcerate: Race and the Growing Reliance of Schools on Artificial Intelligence (AI) Surveillance. *Odis Johnson, Johns Hopkins University*

Artificial Intelligence Is Not Immune to Sociopolitical Failures. *Ezekiel J. Dixon-Roman, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Emancipatory Data Science & Artificial Intelligence: Historicizing Data for Equitable AI Futures. *Thema Monroe-White, George Mason University*

Chairs: *Edmund W. Gordon, Teachers College, Columbia University; Malik Boykin, Brown University*

Discussants: *Prudence L. Carter, Brown University; Ebony O. McGee, Johns Hopkins University*

AERA Research and Science Policy Sessions

57.017. Early Career Research Fellowship and Funding Opportunities. AERA Science and Policy Sessions; Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 511C; 1:45-3:15pm

Chair: *George L. Wimberly, American Educational Research Association*

Participants: *Jack Busbee, National Academy of Education; Rhoda Freelon, The Spencer Foundation; Jenny Irons, William T. Grant Foundation*

57.018. The Perspectives of Deans on Navigating Graduate Student and Early Career Trajectories: An Open Discussion. AERA Science and Policy Sessions; Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 502A; 1:45-3:15pm

Chair: *Kathryn B. Chval, University of Illinois at Chicago*

Participants: *Jack H. Knott, New York University; Stephanie J. Rowley, University of Virginia; Frank Hernandez, Texas Christian University; Paula Groves Price, North Carolina A&T State University*

57.019. Unforgetting Histories, Defending Futures: An Interactive Town Hall on Censorship and Democratic Schooling. AERA Science and Policy Sessions; Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 511AB; 1:45-3:15pm

Chairs: *David M. Osher, Education Collaboratory at Yale University; Brenda L. Townsend Walker, University of South Florida*

Participants: *Brenda L. Townsend Walker, University of South Florida; David M. Osher, Education Collaboratory at Yale University; Sameer Sourav, UCLA Community Schools; Pedro A. Noguera, University of Southern California; Angela Lopez, UCLA Community Schools; Mark Rosenbaum, Public Counsel; Megan Bang, Northwestern University*

Committee Sessions

57.020. Division H Fireside Chat: (Re)memory: Understanding Assessment Past and Liberating Testing Tomorrow.

Graduate Student Council Cosponsored with Division H - Research, Evaluation and Assessment in Schools; Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 402A; 1:45-3:15pm

Chair: *Omayya Horton, University of Massachusetts - Amherst*

Panelists: *Carol D. Lee, Northwestern University; Jennifer Randall, University of Michigan; Kyndra V. Middleton, Howard University*

Division Sessions

57.021. Superintendent Leadership and Retention. Division A - Administration; Paper Session

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, San Fernando; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Falling Off a Cliff: Gendered Turnover Trends in the Superintendency. *Jennifer Timmer, Seton Hall University; David S Woo, University of Utah*

Latina Superintendents Occupy Their Liminal Space to Empower and Transform Rural and Mid-size School Districts. *Zoraya Davidson, Texas Tech Alumni; Jeong-Hee Kim, Texas Tech University; David Johnston, Texas Tech University; Randi Wold-Brennon, Texas Tech University; Aileen Narido Hermes, Texas Tech University*

Leading Through the Margins: The Experiences of Latina Superintendents in California. *Charity Lourdes Castro, University of California - Los Angeles*

Systems in Motion: A Superintendent of Color Rewrites the Script of Adaptive Leadership. *Karika Ann Parker, Western Michigan University*

Beyond Implementation: Superintendents as Context-Sensitive AI Leaders in K-12 Schools. *Soon-young Oh, Michigan State University*

Chair: *Karina Guerrero, Claremont Graduate University*

Discussant: *Victoria Koop, Wichita State University*

57.022. Attacked Because It Works: Defending the Power of Ethnic Studies in California. Division B - Curriculum Studies; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304A;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

What They're Really Afraid Of: The Radical Power of Ethnic Studies. *Allyson Tintiangco-Cubales, San Francisco State University*
Access as a Liberatory Principle of Ethnic Studies: Supporting Multiply-Marginalized Black and Brown Youth. *Subini Ancy Annamma, Stanford University; Aimee Riechel, San Francisco State University*
Teacher Education and the Fight for Ethnic Studies Amongst Conservative Backlash. *Rita Kohli, University of California - Riverside*
Centering the Four Cornerstones: Ensuring Principled Implementation of Ethnic Studies Teacher Development. *Arnelson Concordia, Santa Barbara Unified School District*
Chair: *Maharaj Desai, California State University - East Bay*
Discussant: *Arlene Daus-Magboul, San Francisco State University*

57.023. Bridging Gaps: AI and Digital Learning for Diverse Learners. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Palos Verdes; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Adapting Interactive Digital Materials for Learners with Intellectual and Developmental Disabilities. *Shamila Janakiraman, University of Hawai'i at Mānoa; Robin Dazzeo, University of Hawaii - Manoa; Sandra Oshiro, University of Hawaii - Manoa*
Adaptive AI for Science Text Accessibility in Students with Reading Disabilities. *Richard Lamb, University of Georgia; Danielle Jo Malone, Purdue University; Tosha L. Owens, East Carolina University; Ikseon Choi, Emory University; Shruti Kundu, University of Georgia*
Digital Technology as Amplifier and Buffer of SES-Achievement Gap: Evidence from Double Machine Learning. *Yigu Liang, Beijing Normal University; Na Li, Beijing Normal University; Yingke Xu, Beijing Normal University; Wei Tian, Beijing Normal University*
Middle school Black Girls' Perspectives on Surveillance: Discourse Shifts in a Critical Machine Learning Project. *Atefeh Behboudi, Vanderbilt University; Golnaz Arastoopour Irgens, Vanderbilt University*
Promoting Science Learning Among At-Risk Students: The Impact of Exploratory Learning Utilizing Interactive Simulations. *Janan Saba, Hebrew University of Jerusalem; Malak Abu Rmaileh, Hebrew University of Jerusalem; Tali Gal, Hebrew University of Jerusalem*
Chair: *Elnara Mammadova, Purdue University*

57.024. Fostering Engagement for All: Advancing Socioculturally Inclusive Theory, Research, and Practice in Student Engagement. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Workshop
Westin Bonaventure, Level 3, Hollywood Ballroom; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

School Dropout Process from a Sociocultural Lens: A Life-Course Engagement-Resilience Model for Immigrant-Background Students. *Isabelle Archambault, University of Montréal; Véronique Dupéré, University of Montréal; Sophie Pascal, University of Montréal; Kristel Tardif-Grenier; Michel Janosz, University of Montreal*
Reframing Engagement: A Sociocultural Approach to Learning, Behavioral Climate, and Developmental Equity. *Christina Scanlon, University of Chicago; James P. Huguley, University of Pittsburgh; Ming-Te Wang, University of Chicago*
Parent Socialization of Student Engagement: The Role of Culture, Ethnicity, and Socioeconomic Status. *Jennifer A. Fredricks, Union College*
Teacher Influences on Student Engagement: Integrating the Classic, the Current, and the Cultural. *Gregory Arief D. Liem, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University*
Mapping Belonging and Moving from the Monolithic to the Malleable: Implications for Student Engagement. *Kelly-Ann Allen, Monash University; Christopher Boyle, University of Adelaide*
Cultural Pathways to Flow: Parental Influences Shaping Engagement in Learning. *David J. Shernoff, Rutgers University; Janine Bempechat, Boston University*
Agentic Engagement: Sociocultural Supports and Thwarts. *Johnmarshall Reeve, Australian Catholic University; Hyungshim Jang, Hanyang University*
Student Momentary Engagement in the Life Course: A Sociocultural Developmental Perspective. *Jennifer Symonds, University College London; Benjamin M. Torsney, Temple University; Ioannis Katsantonis, University of Cambridge; Natassa Kyriakopoulou, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens; Jonathan Smith, Université de Sherbrooke*
A Stridently Situative Approach to Inclusive Engagement and Assessment. *Daniel T. Hickey, Indiana University; Charmian Lam, University of Chicago; Qianxu Morgan Luo, Indiana University*
Critical Racial Third Spaces: Attending to Racialized Realities to Honor Student Engagement. *Crystal Charity, University of Maryland; Rolonda L. Payne, University of Maryland*
Sociocultural Considerations for Engagement in Out-of-School Programs. *Ashlee Lester Sjogren, University of Virginia; Nancy L. Deutsch, University of Virginia*
Chairs: *Gregory Arief D. Liem, National Institute of Education -*

Nanyang Technological University; Jennifer A. Fredricks, Union College

57.025. Human–AI Collaboration in Learning: Dialogue, Inquiry, and Facilitation Patterns. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, San Gabriel B; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Comparative Analysis of Dialogic Patterns between Human and AI Tutors in Online Learning Contexts. *So-Yeon Ahn, KAIST; Suin Kim, Elice; Jieun Han, Korea Advanced Institute of Science and Technology; Junyeong Park, Korea Advanced Institute of Science and Technology; Alice Oh, Korea Advanced Institute of Science and Technology*

Facilitating Disciplinary Reasoning in Online Collaborative Problem Solving: A Mixed Methods Study. *Jessica Andrews Todd, Educational Testing Service; Yvonne Lai, University of Nebraska - Lincoln; Yang Jiang, Educational Testing Service; Edith Aurora Graf, Educational Testing Service; Amy Been Bennett, University of Nebraska - Lincoln; Rachel Funk, University of Nebraska - Lincoln; Colby Lamb, University of Nebraska - Lincoln; Nicole Marienau, University of Nebraska - Lincoln*

Generative AI in Collaborative Learning: A Systematic Review. *Sunyoung Kim, Korea University; Jiyeon Jung, Korea University; Insook Han, Korea University*

Learners' Collaboration With AI in Enhancing Peer Feedback in Argumentative Writing: An Exploratory Study. *Wenli Chen, Nanyang Technological University - National Institute of Education; Xuanyu Chen, Fudan University; Lishan Zheng, Nanyang Technological University - National Institute of Education; Qianru Lyu, Nanyang Technological University - National Institute of Education; Guo Su, Nanyang Technological University - National Institute of Education; Xinmei Kong, Nanyang Technological University - National Institute of Education*

The Role of Group Interaction Patterns in Shaping Learning Outcomes in AR-Enhanced Collaborative Inquiry. *Xinyue Jiao, New York University; Zifeng Liu, University of Florida; Su Cai, Beijing Normal University*

Chair: *Joey Huang, North Carolina State University*

57.026. Critical and Culturally Conscious Engagement with Generative AI in Qualitative Research. Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Symposium
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 7th Floor, Hollywood Ballroom I; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Beyond Efficiency: A Triadic Framework for AI-Assisted Qualitative Inquiry Honoring Researcher Sovereignty. *Kakali Bhattacharya, University of Florida*

Disrupting AI Mythologies: From Deus Ex Machina to Echosocial Partnerships in Qualitative Research. *Leia K.*

Cain, University of Tennessee

Technological Reflexivity in Practice: Navigating Generative AI in Qualitative Research. *Jessica Nina Lester, Indiana University*

Troubling the Platform: Concerns with AI for QDA. *Johmy Saldaña, Arizona State University*

Chairs: *Leia K. Cain, University of Tennessee; Kakali Bhattacharya, University of Florida*

Discussants: *Johmy Saldaña, Arizona State University; Jessica Nina Lester, Indiana University; Kakali Bhattacharya, University of Florida; Leia K. Cain, University of Tennessee*

57.027. Examining the Politics of Curriculum and its Influence. Division F - Historical Inquiry in Education; Paper Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 501B; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Divided Lands, Calculated Erasures: Indian Boarding School Mathematics as a Tool of Settler Colonialism. *Mary Smith, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; José Francisco Gutiérrez, University of Utah; Cynthia Benally, University of Utah*

Unforgetting the History of Elementary Composition in US Schools 1900-1950. *Joan M. Taylor, University of Nevada - Reno*

The Enduring Echoes of a Citizen School: Lessons from Porto Alegre for Democratic Futures in Education. *Luis Armando Gandin, Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Sul*

Spencerian Protestantism and Racial Complementarity: P.V.N. Myers and American Secondary World History Education, 1871-1921. *Stephen J. Jackson, University of Kansas*

Communicating War within Topaz, Mary Fujii's Melancholic Speech, "Home Without a Fence" in 1943. *Vivian Bo Kyung Lee, University of Utah*

Chair: *Jill M Sullivan, Arizona State University*

Discussant: *Ann Marie Ryan, University of Texas - San Antonio*

57.028. Freedom Dreaming Towards Ethnic Studies in Tumultuous Times: Teacher-and-Researcher Reflections on Race, Pedagogy, and Power. Division G - Social Context of Education; Symposium

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 301B; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Feasibility of Middle School Ethnic Studies Implementation. *Gabriela López, Stanford University*

Classroom Cultures of Love, Living, and Learning: A Portraiture of Life-Affirming Pedagogical Rituals in Ethnic Studies Lessons. *Natalie Hibdon, San Francisco Unified School District*

Cultivating Knowledge of Self Through Autoethnography and Community Listening Parties in Middle School Ethnic Studies. *Elias Bautista, San Francisco Unified School*

District

Rethinking Social Studies: Expanding Students' Worldview through the Integration of Ethnic Studies. *Kathryn Marcouiller, San Francisco Unified School District*

Ethnic Studies Pedagogical Horizons: Educators' Reflections on Desired Skills, Standpoints, and Content Knowledge of Incoming Students. *Darion A. Wallace, Stanford University*

Discussant: *Farima Pour-Khorshid, University of San Francisco*

57.029. Interrogating the Social Contexts of Higher Education.

Division G - Social Context of Education; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 303B;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

International Graduate Students' Experiences with DEI Programs at a U.S. University: A Study on Their Social Communication. *Hongwei Yang, University of West Florida; Jian Su, The University of Tennessee - Knoxville; Edward Okai-Boafo, University of West Florida; Kwame Owusu Daaku, University of West Florida*

Pedagogies of Embodied Resistance: Creating Borderlands for Collective Healing in Psychology Education. *Emese Ilyés, John Jay College of Criminal Justice*

Resting While They Retaliate: A Black Feminist Reflection on Joy, Survival, and Institutional Betrayal in Mid-Level Management at a Predominantly White Institution. *Anglesia Brown, Wayne State University*

Understanding the Role of Mentoring High School Students and STEM Identity Among Underrepresented Undergraduate Students. *Sabina Iturralde, University of Arizona; Yamini Sumalatha Bhukya, University of Arizona; Qianqian Wang, University of Arizona; Jessica J. Summers, University of Arizona*

Chair: *Hyacinth T Campbell, Brock University*

Discussant: *Ting-Han Chang, William Paterson University*

57.030. Male Teachers of Color in the Social Context of

Education. Division G - Social Context of Education; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 303A;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

La Loteria and Creative Resistance Origins from 2015 to 2025; Epistemology, Practical Methodologies, for students and teachers of color. *Luis Genaro Garcia, California State University - Sacramento*

(Re)membering the History of Asian American Male Teachers. *Lin Wu, Western Oregon University*

Reframing Presence: Male Teachers of Color with Disabilities in the Social Context of Education. *Antonio L. Ellis, American University*

Faith, Family, and Football: Black Men Teachers' Influences and Aims for Teaching. *Terrance Joshua Lewis, University of Alabama*

Chair: *Travis J. Bristol, University of California - Berkeley*

Discussant: *Lasana D. Kazembe, Indiana University - Indianapolis*

57.031. Wellness, Healing, Joy, and Resistance at the Intersections of Racial, Gender, and Sexual Identities.

Division G - Social Context of Education; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 401;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Curricular Haints and The African American Storytelling Tradition: Method, Mirror, and Map of Ancestral Resistance. *Lisa Marie Westbrooks, Wayne State University*

Afrofuturism as a Radical Praxis for Black Educator Wellness. *Nadia A. Clarke-Cordick, University of Guelph-Humber*

Get Outsiders Outside: Inclusive Outdoor Adventure Education for Healing from Gender and Racialized Stereotypes. *Nicole Kangas, Sacramento City Unified School District*

Latine/x LGBTQ+ TikTok Counterspaces as Learning Communities Fostering Counternarratives and Intersectional Identities. *Gloriana Lopez-Leon, University of California - Santa Cruz; Saskias Casanova, University of California - Santa Cruz*

Queer Joy as a Pedagogy of Resistance: Reimagining Gender-based Violence Prevention with LGBTQ+ Student Educators. *JJ Wright, MacEwan University*

Discussant: *Harper B. Keenan, University of British Columbia*

57.032. Division H VP Session: Past Designs, Present Tensions, Future Paths: Reimagining Educational Assessment

Across Contexts. Division H - Research, Evaluation and Assessment in Schools; Structured Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 515A;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

1. From General Quality Assurance to Strict Quality Control? A Case Study of Flemish Educational Policy (Poster 1). *Rianne Janssen, KU Leuven*

2. Gendered STEM Career Aspirations and Tracking Effects: Cross-National Insights from PISA 2022 Germany and U.S. (Poster 2). *Haofei Li, The Ohio State University*

3. Data-Based School Development? Longitudinal Findings on the Relationship Between School Improvement Activities and Student Achievement in Austria (Poster 3). *Jana Groß Ophoff, Thurgau University of Teacher Education; David Kemethofer, University of Teacher Education Upper Austria; Christoph Helm, Johannes Kepler University of Linz; Ramona Zintl, IQS – Federal Institute for Quality Assurance of the Austrian School System; Martina Ott, University College of Teacher Education Vorarlberg; Katharina Meusbürger, University College of Teacher Education Vorarlberg*

4. Student Engagement in International Large-Scale Assessments under the PIRLS 2021 Group Adaptive Design (Poster 4). *Alec Kennedy, IEA Hamburg; Yuan-Ling Liaw,*

IEA Hamburg

5. Feedback Flows: How Teachers' Experiences Receiving Feedback Shape Their Classroom Practices (Poster 5). *Brendha Christie Tanujaya, Purdue University; Shahnaz Safitri, Purdue University; Nielsen Pereira, Purdue University/Gifted Education Research & Resource Institute*
 6. Portfolios and Public Presentations as an Assessment Culture in a Charter High School (Poster 6). *Natalie Neugebauer Schoettler, Auburn University; David T. Marshall, Auburn University; Tim Pressley, Christopher Newport University*
 7. Comprehensive Assessment in Mathematics Education: Exploring Practices, Challenges, and Recommendations (Poster 7). *Divya Gautam, Indian Institute Of Technology Gandhinagar; Sneha Abhishek, Indian Institute of Technology Gandhinagar*
- Chairs: *Paul Campbell, The University of Hong Kong; Evelyn Goffin, University of Antwerp; Deepak Sharma, Indian Institute of Management*

57.033. Design Matters: Implications of Institutional Enactment of State and Federal Policies. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum H; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Beyond the First Semester: Longitudinal Effects of Corequisite Course Design in Texas. *Christine Mokher, Florida State University; Toby Park-Gaghan, Florida State University*

"Strict or Stricter" Makes Bad SAP (Policy): A Critical Assessment of Financial Aid Satisfactory Academic Progress Policies. *Zach Taylor, John Burton Advocates for Youth; Sarah Pauter, John Burton Advocates for Youth; Karla A. Weber Wandel, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Understanding Institutional Responses to Student Return on Investment Policy Mandates in North Carolina. *Kristin Villanueva, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Ramatu Issifu, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Sandra L. Dika, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Carl Westine, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Onima Vadakke Thodiyil, University of North Carolina - Charlotte*

Are We Shortchanging Some Undergraduates? An Examination of Off-Campus Living Allowances and Retention. *Kara Graham, The Ohio State University; Minjung Kim, The Ohio State University*

Are We Shortchanging Some Undergraduates? An Examination of Off-Campus Living Allowances and Poverty. *Kara Graham, The Ohio State University*

Chair: *Jerry M. Whitmore, Boston University*

Discussant: *Brian Holzman, Texas A&M University*

57.034. Improving Student Success in Online Dual Enrollment Courses through the Increasing College Access Network. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Symposium

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum G; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Resources that Support Dual Enrollment Course Innovation. *Leah Eggers, Jobs for the Future*

Leveraging Technical Assistance and Community Building to Sustain SEL-based Dual Enrollment Courses. *Ashley Fellows, FullScale; Steven Walvig, Greater Twin Cities United Way*

Evaluating the Implementation of the Increasing College Access Network. *Kellie Mayer, American Institutes for Research*

Meeting Students Where They Are: Evaluating the Impact of the Increasing College Access Network. *Uttara Balakrishnan, American Institutes for Research; Kristina L. Zeiser, American Institutes for Research*

Chair: *Anna O'Connor, Jobs for the Future*

Discussant: *Anna O'Connor, Jobs for the Future*

57.035. Strengthening STEM Pathways: Strategies for Supporting Students from Low-Income Backgrounds at HBCUs. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum F; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Bridging Access and Completion: A Model for STEM Scholars from Low-Income Backgrounds at an HBCU. *Grant Wanjala Wangila, University of Arkansas at Pine Bluff*

Biotechnology Pathways: Leveraging Mentorship and Workforce Experience to Advance STEM Students from Low-Income Backgrounds. *Sarwan Dhir, Fort Valley State University*

Engineering Experiences: Developing Leaders in Computer Science and Engineering through Holistic Support. *Claude Turner, Norfolk State University*

Key Predictors of Engaged Learning Among S-STEM Engineering Students at an HBCU. *Jing Yan, Tennessee State University; Xia Zhao, Tennessee State University; Lin Li, Tennessee State University*

Chair: *Ivory A. Toldson, Howard University*

Discussants: *Mercy Mugo, Qem Network; Brittany Boyd, American Institutes for Research*

57.036. Emerging Considerations for Designing In-Service Teacher Training in Generative AI. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 9; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

AI Assessment Scale (AIAS) in Practice: Analyzing Teacher Engagement with Ethical AI Use in Online Professional Development. *Selcuk Dogan, Georgia Southern University; Nihan Agacli Dogan, Georgia Southern University*

Embodying Justice & Designing Futures: K-12 Teachers'

Engagement with AI and Social Justice Pedagogy. *Eric R. Junco, Northern Illinois University; Razak Kwame Dwomoh, Northern Illinois University; Hyoju Ahn, Northern Illinois University*

Evaluating The Impact of Digital Teacher Training on Generative AI Adoption in Urban Chinese Schools. *William Edusei-Mensah, Beijing Normal University; Yushun Li, Beijing Normal University; Jiannan Bai, Beijing Normal University*

Factors Affecting Vocational Teachers' Adoption of Generative AI: A Multigroup Analysis by Discipline and Region. *Yiran Cui, Shandong University; Meng Li, China National Academy of Educational Sciences*

Reimagining World Language Teaching: AI Integration and Professional Development for K-12 Educators. *Junye Guo, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

Discussant: *Panagiotis Kosmas, University of Limassol - Cyprus*

57.037. Purpose and Power: Black Women Educators' Legacies, Resistance, and Futures. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 8; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Engineering Hair: Unveiling STEM Through Critical Experiential Learning with Elementary Black Girls, Their Families, and Educators. *Brittany Nicole Anderson, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Ginaya Littlejohn, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Sydney Carroll, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Tierra M. Parsons, University of North Carolina - Charlotte*

Racism, Resilience, and Resistance: Black Educators' Persistence in the Teaching Profession. *Nia F Ladson, Drexel University*

Unforgetting and ReImagining: Exploring Abbott Elementary's Impact on a Black Woman Pre-Service Teacher's Developing Identity. *Sara Ann Jones, Illinois State University; Mariah D. Harmon, Pennsylvania State University*

Unforgetting Our Legacy: Examining the Enduring Impact of Black Women Educators. *Shanique Lee, Rutgers University*

Chair: *Tehia Starker Glass, University of North Carolina - Charlotte*

Discussant: *Tianna Dowie-Chin, University of Georgia*

57.038. Radical Imagination and Collective Disruption: Reimagining Teacher Education through Community Partnerships. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 1; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Becoming Social Justice, Culturally Sustaining Educators: Career Changer Pathways in Teacher Education. *Ani C.*

Moughamian-Rosenberg, Saint Mary's College of California
Collective Disruption and Transformation: Responsivity and Emergence in Rural Teacher Education. *Terry Taylor, University of British Columbia; Leyton Schnellert, University of British Columbia; Jamilee Baroud, University of British Columbia; Amy Caesar, University of British Columbia; Samantha Sinanan, The University of British Columbia*

Cultivating reflective practice, leadership, and adaptive expertise: A case study of school-based clinical practices. *Carrie Eunyoung Hong, William Paterson University; Michelle Gonzalez, William Paterson University*

Radical Imagination and Critical Pedagogy in Teacher Exploration: A Community College-High School Partnership. *Leticia Rojas, Pasadena City College; Haley Castello, Pasadena City College; Diego Varela, Pasadena City College*

Uncomfortable Truths: Exploring Pushback to Racial Equity in a Teacher Education Program. *Bernadette Castillo, University of Houston; Beth Beschorner, Minnesota State University - Mankato; David Kimori, Minnesota State University - Mankato*

57.039. Teachers' Decision Making in Precarious Contexts. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 7; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Attrition as Resistance Among Black Male Educators: When Departure Speaks. *Roslin E. Growe, University of Louisiana at Lafayette; Clementine Msengi, Lamar University; Heather Jones*

Do Not Obey in Advance: Teachers co-construction and instruction of ambiguous or authoritarian policy language. *Sara Michael-Luna, University of Central Florida; Michele Lynn Regalla, University of Central Florida*

The Experiences of Elementary School Educators Who Remain Working in Schools That Serve Marginalized Communities. *Maxine Cameron, New York City Public Schools*

"The Only Spokesperson On The Entire Campus": Palestinian American Teacher Identity and Critical Consciousness. *Hanadi Shatara, California State University - Sacramento; Rebeca Ayala, California State University, Sacramento*

Chair: *Roslin E. Growe, University of Louisiana at Lafayette*
Discussant: *Brandon L. Fox, University of Wisconsin Stevens Point*

57.040. Unplugged CT as Essential Learning Practices: Examples from Elementary Contexts. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 6; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Decomposition Demystified: An Exploratory Learning Progression for Integrating Decomposition in Elementary School Lessons. *Maggie Vanderberg, Southern Oregon University; Dylana Garfas, Ashland School District*

Hidden Frameworks: What Summaries of Goldilocks Reveal About the Process of Abstraction. *Eping Hung, Southern Oregon University*

Once Upon an Algorithm: Computational Thinking Through the Stories We Tell. *Kelly Renae Martin, Ashland School District; Gladys Krause, College of William & Mary*

Where is Everybody in the Everybody Books?: Representation in K-5 Picture Books. *Trish Yoshiko Dorr, Ashland School District*

Lessons Learned: Integrating Computational Thinking in Multilingual Classrooms Across Contexts. *Jennifer Mohatt, Phoenix Talent School District; Dylana Garfas, Ashland School District*

Chair: *Eva Skuratowicz, Southern Oregon University*

Discussant: *Jill Hubbard, Oregon State University - Cascades*

57.041. Measuring Impact, Imagining Futures: What Works (and Doesn't) in Education Reform. Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 2; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Building Equitable Futures: A Multi-State High-Dosage Tutoring Data Toolkit. *Jason Godfrey, Harvard University; Rebecca Marshall, Harvard University; Matthew P. Steinberg, George Mason University*

Can an Extremely Segregated School System Foster Integration? Evidence from the Chilean Case. *Juan Pablo Valenzuela, Universidad de Chile; Claudio Allende, Universidad de Chile; Francisco Meneses, Universidad de Chile; Tomás Ilabaca, Universidad de Playa Ancha*

Context, mechanisms and outcomes of accountability policies; a comparative review of 14 systems. *Melanie Ehren, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam; loic menzies, University of Cambridge; Alison O'Mara-Eves, University College London - IOE; Simon Antonia, University College London - IOE*

Unfulfilled Expectations for Equitable Schools & Education Futures: Findings from the CA Multi-Tiered System of Support (MTSS) Scale Up. *Brian Huff, University of California - Los Angeles; Joseph P. Bishop, University of California - Los Angeles*

What Works (and Doesn't Work) for Closing Achievement Gaps? Comparative Meta-Analysis of Educational Intervention Approaches. *Jaekyung Lee, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Kenneth K. Wong, Brown University*

Chair: *Kenneth K. Wong, Brown University*

Discussant: *Alex J. Bowers, Teachers College, Columbia University*

57.042. Shifting Paradigms: Understanding Critical Policy Analysis as a Lens for Equity-Focused Education Policy Research. Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Symposium

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 10; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Conceptualizing Equity and Justice in Education Policy Research: A Unifying Framework and Systematic Review of the Literature. *Meghan Comstock, University of Maryland; Nora Reikosky, University of Houston; Cody Norton, University of Maryland*

Teacher Educators as Policy Actors: Navigating the Racial Politics of Culturally Responsive-Sustaining Education Teaching Standards. *Maya Kaul, University of Pennsylvania; Meghan Comstock, University of Maryland; Joy Esboldt, University of Delaware*

Equity in Process: Inhibiting School Leaders' Equitable Practices within the School Improvement Planning Process. *Latrice Marianno, Southern Illinois University - Edwardsville*

From Saviorism to Solidarity: White and Middle-Class Parents Reimagining Public Education. *Talia S. Leibovitz, University of California - Berkeley*

A Critical Policy History Analysis of Student-Led Resistance Against Houston ISD State Takeover Policy. *Alison Wilson, University of Houston; Detra DeVerne Johnson, University of Houston*

Chair: *Maya Kaul, University of Pennsylvania*

Discussant: *Sarah Diem, University of Missouri*

SIG Sessions

57.043. Building Teacher Capacity for AI: Self-Efficacy, Pedagogy, and Professional Development. SIG-Advanced Technologies for Learning; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Level 3, Santa Monica B; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Teachers' Views on Integrating AI in K-12 Education: Insights from East Tennessee. *Rachel Min Wong, University of Tennessee; Joan Williams, University of Tennessee; Sondra LoRe, STEM Program Evaluation, Assessment & Research (SPEAR); Lynn L. Hodge, University of Tennessee; Catherine Schuman, University of Tennessee*

Assessing Faculty Confidence in Using Generative AI to Teach 21st Century Skills. *Armanto Sutedjo, Texas A&M University; Stephanie Liu, Texas A&M University; Mahjabin Chowdhury, Texas A&M University; Debra Fowler, Texas A&M University*

How Science Teachers' Pedagogical Orientations and School Contexts Shape GenAI Use. *Sarah Nielsen, WestEd; Drew Nucci, WestEd*

Enhancing K-12 Educators' Coding and Computational

Thinking Skills and Values with a GenAI-Supported Online Module. *Seoljoo Kang, Purdue University; Wanju Huang, Purdue University*

Advancing Civic Education with AI: A Multi-Theoretical Framework for Digital Storytelling. *Lei Wang, Auburn University - Montgomery*

Discussant: *Mahjabin Chowdhury, Texas A&M University*

57.044. Reimagining the Future of Bilingual Teacher Education: Community and Field Visions, Policies, Pedagogies, and Praxis. SIG-Bilingual Education Research; Structured Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 515B;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

1. El Arte as Traveling Embodiment of Critical Consciousness: “Se Hace el Camino al Andar” (Poster 1). *Lucia Cardenas Curiel, Michigan State University; Lindsay M. McHolme, Georgia State University*
2. Building Capacity for Asian Dual Language Programs: Insights from Korean Bilingual Teacher Preparation (Poster 2). *Grace Cho, California State University - Fullerton; Lyn Scott, California State University - East Bay*
3. More than Language and Literacy: Heritage Language Teachers’ Desires and Needs for Ethnic Studies Preparation (Poster 3). *Jenna Cushing-Leubner, University of Wisconsin - Whitewater; Natalia Benjamin, Rochester Public Schools*
4. Preparing Teachers to Foster Multilingual Learners’ Ideas: Language and Pedagogy in Pre-service Teacher Education (Poster 4). *George C. Bunch, University of California - Santa Cruz; Benjamin M. James, University of Delaware*
5. Translanguaging as a Powerful Source for Developing a Multilingual Writerly Voice (Poster 5). *Cecilia M. Espinosa, Lehman College - CUNY; Laura Ascenzi-Moreno, Brooklyn College - CUNY*
6. Passing the Buck... To Whom?: Deconstructing Exclusion towards Reimagined Bilingual Education (Poster 6). *María Cioe-Pena, University of Pennsylvania; Diana Lalata, University of Pennsylvania*
7. Addressing the Shortage: Expanding Asian Language Bilingual Teacher Education in California’s Dual Language Programs (Poster 7). *Natalie A. Tran, California State University - Fullerton*
8. Nurturing the Complex and Dynamic Nature of Bilingual and Biliterate Development in Early Childhood (Poster 8). *Nelia Peña, University of Colorado - Boulder; Mileidis Gort, University of Colorado - Boulder*
9. Nurturing Identity Through Latinx Children’s Literature in Bilingual Teacher Education (Poster 9). *Luz Yadira Herrera, California State University - Dominguez Hills*

Discussant: *Carla España, Brooklyn College - CUNY*

57.045. Encuentros, Pláticas, y Testimonios for Imagining New

Visions of Early Childhood Research. SIG-Critical Perspectives on Early Childhood Education; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 301A;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Co-constructing and Designing an Early Learning Alliance Evaluation: Elevating Center Director Voice. *Emily A. Diaz, Westat; Larrisa Wilkinson, Pre-K 4 SA; Sarah Nelson Baray, Pre-K 4 SA; Lauren Elizabeth Decker-Woodrow, Westat; Cynthia Castillo, Pre-K 4 SA*

Resistencia A Través de Conocimiento (Resistance Through Knowing): Countervisuality Within the “Fateful Triangle”. *Thania Gómez-Martínez, Bank Street College of Education; Xiaohan Yang Zhu, Texas A&M University; Mark Nagasawa, Bank Street College of Education; Franklin S. Aucapina, New York Hall of Science; Diana Ballesteros, Graduate Center - CUNY; Susan M. Letourneau, New York Hall of Science; Cristina M. Medellin, Bank Street College of Education*

I do this Because I Care: Testimonios from Latina Educators, Career Advisors, and Faculty. *Cristina M. Medellin, Bank Street College of Education; Claudine Campanelli, City University of New York*

Sparkling Community Voices to Amplify Mathematical Knowledge. *Dawn Woods, Oakland University*

Using Research to Support Social Change Against Systemic Racism in the Early Educator Workforce. *Yoonjeon Kim, University of California - Berkeley; Hopeton Hess, Center for the Study of Child Care Employment*

Chair: *Mark Nagasawa, Bank Street College of Education*

Discussant: *Diana Ballesteros, Graduate Center - CUNY*

57.046. Language as a Learning Tool: Teacher Talk in Early Math and Literacy. SIG-Early Education and Child Development; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Georgia I;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Embedding Math in Everyday Moments: How Early Childhood Teachers Describe Their Own Math Language. *Emilia Wenzel, University of Chicago*

Investigating the Role of Teacher Sensitive Responsiveness in Children’s English Language Learning. *Michelle Rose Madlansacay, University of Chicago*

Comparing Use of Language-Supportive Strategies During Shared Reading Across Classrooms with Varying Child Language Gains. *Jamlick Bosire, University of Missouri; Hyejin Kim, The Ohio State University; Rachel E. Schachter, University of Illinois at Chicago; Clarielle Gabas, University of Nebraska - Lincoln*

Chair: *Jamlick Bosire, University of Missouri*

Discussant: *Emilia Wenzel, University of Chicago*

57.047. LLM-Driven Innovations in Psychometric Evaluation

and Modeling. SIG-Educational Statisticians; Symposium
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor,
Wilshire Grand Ballroom I; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Leveraging Interview-Informed LLMs to Model Survey Responses: Comparative Insights from AI-Generated and Human Data. *Jihong Zhang, University of Arkansas at Fayetteville; Xinya Liang, University of Arkansas; Nicole Grace Bonge, University of Arkansas at Fayetteville; Anqi Deng, University of Arkansas at Fayetteville; Nicole Zarrett, University of South Carolina; Lin Tan, Virginia Tech*

Variability in AI-Generated Personas: Method Comparison and Psychometric Assessment. *Xinya Liang, University of Arkansas; Jihong Zhang, University of Arkansas at Fayetteville; Chunhua Cao, University of Alabama; Anqi Deng, University of Arkansas at Fayetteville; Nicole Zarrett, University of South Carolina*

Leveraging LLM Tool Calling for Automating Q-Matrix Construction in Cognitive Diagnosis Analysis. *Jihong Zhang, University of Arkansas at Fayetteville*

Text-Based Approaches to Classification of Item Difficulty Levels. *Hong Jiao, University of Maryland; Sydney Peters, University of Maryland; Hanna Choi, Ewha Womans University; Qingshu XU, Hunan Normal University*

LLM-Enhanced Automated Item Content Analysis Supporting CAT Applications. *Jing Huang, Purdue University; Jihong Zhang, University of Arkansas at Fayetteville; Hua-Hua Chang, Purdue University*

Chair: *Xinya Liang, University of Arkansas*

Discussant: *Alina A. Von Davier, Duolingo*

57.048. Centering Learners, Culture, and Care: Enacting Culturally Responsive Practices through University-Community Engagement. SIG-Experiential Education and Community Engagement: Scholarship and Practice; Symposium

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Georgia II; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Experiential Activity with Math CEO: Connecting Data and Life Stories through Culturally Responsive Teaching. *Alessandra Pantano, University of California - Irvine; Cynthia Sanchez Tapia, California State University - Dominguez Hills*

Culturally Responsive Practices: A Sociocultural Framework for Community-Engaged Learning. *Taylor Michelle Wycoff, University of California - Irvine; Sandra D. Simpkins, University of California - Irvine*

Empowering Students of Different Ages Through Affirming Language in a Community-Engaged Bilingual Science Program. *Jasmine M. Nation, California Polytechnic State University - San Luis Obispo; Alejandra Yep, California Polytechnic State University - San Luis Obispo; Perla Ramos Carranza, California Polytechnic State University -*

San Luis Obispo; Xavier Aguilar, California State Polytechnic University - San Luis Obispo; Isaiah Rivera, California State Polytechnic University - San Luis Obispo; Jessica Garcia-Tapia, California Polytechnic State University - San Luis Obispo; Thais Malfavon, California Polytechnic State University - San Luis Obispo

Investigating Participatory Action-research as a Culturally Responsive Approach to Intergenerational Education in an Immigrant Community. *Laura Vega Hernandez, San Jose State University; Ellen Middaugh, San Jose State University; Mark K. Felton, San José State University*

Chairs: *John Cano, University of California - Berkeley; Mara Welsh Mahmood, University of California - Berkeley*

Discussant: *Marjorie E. Faulstich Orellana, University of California - Los Angeles*

57.049. Examining Informal Practice: Pedagogical Innovations Toward Equity in Informal Education. SIG-Informal Learning Environment Research; Paper Session

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, La Cienega; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

“Far More Excitement than Anxiety”: Teacher Perceptions of Human Capital When Planning Field Trips. *Kristen Kay Fink, Clemson University; Naomi Gerakios Mucci, Clemson University*

From Silos to Systems: Cultivating Collective Agency Among Museum Practitioners. *Susan M. Letourneau, New York Hall of Science; Dana Schloss, New York Hall of Science; Sylvia Perez, The New York Hall of Science; Franklin S. Aucapina, New York Hall of Science; Laycca Umer, New York Hall of Science; Satbir Multani, New York Hall of Science; Amelia Merker, New York Hall of Science; Emilio Bautista, New York Hall of Science; Iboun Morrison, New York Hall of Science; Katherine Ziff, New York Hall of Science; Phebe Chew, New York Hall of Science; Leah Persram, New York Hall of Science; Michael Baburyan, New York Hall of Science; Ralph Emrick, New York Hall of Science; Christiana Stawasz, New York Hall of Science*

Science as a Thousand Stories: Informal Science Educators' Activist Positions and Stances. *Shaghig Chaparian, New York University; Olivia Ortiz, New York University; Kam Waugh, New York University; Wendy Barrales, John Jay College, City University of New York (CUNY); Luz Velasco Vela, BioBus; Jasmine Y. Ma, New York University; Latasha Wright, BioBus; Maia Yoshida, New York University; Ronni Hayden, University of Colorado - Boulder*

The Pedagogical Approaches Educators at Science Museums and Centers Apply and Associated Desired Learner Outcomes. *Analisa Duran, Philip & Patricia Frost Museum of Science; Remy Dou, University of Miami*

Chair: *Susan M. Letourneau, New York Hall of Science*

57.050. AI in K-12 Education. SIG-Instructional Technology;

Paper Session

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Santa Barbara C; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Learning by Teaching AI (LBT-AI): A case of using Teachable Machine as a cognitive tool. *Woei Hung, University of North Dakota; Jordan Trotter, Surrey Elementary School*

Levels of Generative AI Integration in K–12 Education. *Yunjo An, University of North Texas; Shadarra James, University of North Texas*

From Emotion to Learning: How Teachable Agents' Personality Shapes Math Learning. *Bailing Lyu, University of Utah; Chenglu Li, University of Utah; Hai Li, University of Florida; Gokhan Gulfidan, University of Utah; Linlin Wu, University of Utah; Rui Guo, University of Florida*

Listening to Teachers: Adapting a Microelectronics and AI Curriculum Through Participatory Design. *Lauren Eutsler, University of North Texas; Megan Barnes, University of North Texas; Andrea Ramirez-Salgado, University of Florida; Yessy Eka Ambarwati, University of Florida; Woorin Hwang, University of Florida; Talar Terzian, University of Florida; Anany Sharma, University of Florida; Tamzidul Hoque, University of Kansas; Swarup Bhunia, University of Florida; Pasha Antonenko, University of Florida*

Understanding AI Literacy in Early Adolescence: Predictors of Middle School Students' AI Knowledge. *Xiaoman Wang, Western Michigan University; Bridget Newell, University of Florida; Albert Dieter Ritzhaupt, University of Florida; Christine Wusylko, Kennesaw State University; Loraine Cisternas-Garcia, University of Florida; Priyadharshini Ganapathy Prasad, University of Florida; Angela M. Kohnen, University of Florida; Anthony Botelho, University of Florida; Kevin Cen, University of Florida*

Chair: *Yilang Zhao, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

57.051. Talking Faculty: The Linguistic and Professional Choices of Black Faculty in U.S. Higher Education. SIG-Language and Social Processes; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 504;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

How We Got Here: The Power of Black Faculty's Linguistic & Intellectual Autobiographies. *Kendra Calhoun, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Making Moves: Navigating the Job Market Toward a Sustainable Career. *Aris M. Clemons, University of Tennessee*

Designing Your Life: A Wellness Model For Black Faculty in the Language Sciences. *Joy Peltier, The Ohio State University*

Longevity and Linguistic Matter: The Professional Lives of Black Faculty in the Language Sciences. *Kahdeidra Monét Martin, Vassar College*

The Language and Literacy of Black Leadership in the Academy. *Anne Charity Hudley, Stanford University*
Chair: *L.J. Randolph, University of Wisconsin - Madison*
Discussant: *Jonathan Rosa, Stanford University*

57.052. Beyond Enrollment: Latinx Belonging, Resilience, and Justice in Higher Education. SIG-Latina/o/x Research Issues; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 4;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

"If You're Latino, You're Not Really Expected to Go to College": Latino Men's Psychosociocultural Resilience. *Catherine Restrepo-Widney, Florida Atlantic University; Cristobal Salinas Jr, Florida Atlantic University; Sara E. Rodriguez, University of Texas - El Paso; Marissa Vasquez, San Diego State University*

Latinas in STEM at a Texas HSI-R1: Brilliant, Underrepresented, and Building Cultural Community. *Liliana Bravo, Texas A&M University; Emma Claudia Perez, Texas A&M University; Elsa M. Gonzalez, Texas A&M University*

Surviving the After: Post-Transfer Life for Queer Latinx Students in Exclusionary Four-Year Institutions. *Armando Zavala, California State University - Channel Islands*

The Pervasiveness of Gender-Based Intimate Partner Violence Among Latinx Community College Students. *Karla Velasco, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

"When all the commuters go home the "H" in HSI goes away": Latine/x Student Experiences. *Suzanne Garcia, California State University - Monterey Bay; Yeritzi Victoria, University of California - Irvine; Laura Flores, California State University - Monterey Bay; Katy Gonzalez Barrom, California State University - Monterey Bay*

Chair: *Talia I. Raya, University of Arizona*

Discussant: *Cassandra Victoria Guzman, Cornell University*

57.053. Democracy and Education: Authoritarianism, Resistance, and Racial Justice. SIG-Law and Education; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum E;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Education, Race, and the Return of Liberal Equality. *Areto A. Imoukhuede, Florida A&M University*

The "Vicious Voter" and Racial Authoritarianism in American Law. *Atiba Ellis, Case Western Reserve University*

Criminalizing Culture: A Critical Race Theory Analysis of Prosecuting Creativity, Community, and Nonconformity. *Darrell D. Jackson, University of Wyoming*

Reconstructing the Right to Protest. *Christian Sundquist, University of Pittsburgh*

Chair: *Areto A. Imoukhuede, Florida A&M University*

Discussants: *Atiba Ellis, Case Western Reserve University; Darrell*

D. Jackson, University of Wyoming; Christian Sundquist, University of Pittsburgh; Areta A. Imoukhuede, Florida A&M University

57.054. Beyond Survival toward Thriving: Emerging Research on Fostering Holistic Teacher Wellbeing. SIG-Lives of Teachers; Working Group Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 501A;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Empowering Early Career Teachers to Thrive: The Role of Purpose, Patience, and Community. *Kristina M. Valtierra, Colorado College*

Supporting Pre-Service LGBTQIA2S+ Teachers in Precarious Times. *MaryJohn R. Pachuta-Rysak, Grand Valley State University; Sarah Chase, Grand Valley State University; Kelly Lormand, Grand Valley State University*

Peer Mentoring Future Special Educators to “Fight the Fight Worth Fighting”. *Shana J. Haines, University of Vermont; Kristabel Stark, University of Vermont; Parker Goss, University of Vermont*

Recruiting and Retaining Special Educator Mentor Teachers: Motivators and Challenges. *Kristabel Stark, University of Vermont; Shana J. Haines, University of Vermont*

Teaching Through Trauma: Supporting Teachers Through Times of Personal Trauma and Loss. *Dulcey Hunter, University of South Florida - Tampa*

Chair: *Kristina M. Valtierra, Colorado College*

57.055. Fostering Belonging and Identity in Middle Level Education: Equity, Empathy, and Engagement. SIG-Middle-Level Education Research; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, La Brea; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Good Teachers as “STAR” Teachers: A Qualitative Study of Contemporary Early Adolescents’ Perspectives. *Pei Wang, Boston University; Tina M. Durand, Boston University; Mitali Temurnikar, Boston University*

Middle Grades Youth Challenging Erasure: Navigating Trust, Knowledge, and Friction in Response to Anti-LGBTQ+ Legislation. *Marisa Segel, Boston College; Kyle P. Smith, University of Michigan*

Pedagogical Wisdom in Challenging Times: How Award-Winning Middle School History Teachers Cultivate Responsive Classrooms. *Elizabeth A. Shaver, North Carolina State University*

The Echoes of Adolescence: Legacy Motivation, Authentic Alignment, and Collective Thriving in Middle School. *Brittany Pecor, University of Louisiana at Lafayette; Amanda S. Mayeaux, University of Louisiana at Lafayette; Marietta Smith Adams, University of Louisiana at Lafayette; Aimee Barber, University of Louisiana at Lafayette*

Chair: *David C. Virtue, Western Carolina University*

Discussant: *Patience Amadu, University of Colorado - Colorado*

Springs

57.056. Exploring the Optimal Use of Motivation Regulation Strategies for Academic Success. SIG-Motivation in Education; Symposium
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, San Gabriel A; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Dynamic Motivation Regulation: Stability, Predictors, and Outcomes of Motivation-Regulation Profiles among Sixth-Grade Students. *Yang-Hsin Fan, University of Texas at Austin; Jing-Yi Shen, Beijing Normal University; Patricia Chen, University of Texas at Austin*

Do Students’ Exam-Specific Motivational Regulation Profiles Differ in Initial Motivation Regulation and Exam-Specific Learning Outcomes? *Serena Luo, The Ohio State University; Kaicheng Zhang, Michigan State University; Cristina D. Zepeda, Vanderbilt University*

How Motivational Regulation Shapes and Is Shaped by Motivational Beliefs Over Time: Time-Lagged Network Analysis. *Yeo-eun Kim, Sungkyunkwan University; Patrick N. Beymer, University of Cincinnati; Emily Quinn Rosenzweig, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Examining Metamotivational Awareness as a Component of Optimal Strategy Use. *Erika Alvarez-Atencio, Universidad Complutense de Madrid; David B. Miele, Boston College; Jesús M. Alvarado, Universidad Complutense de Madrid; David B. Miele, Boston College*

Chairs: *Yang-Hsin Fan, University of Texas at Austin; Patricia Chen, University of Texas at Austin; David B. Miele, Boston College*

Discussant: *Markus Dresel, University of Augsburg*

57.057. Real insights from real classrooms: Motivation scholars’ experiences designing for and working with observational data. SIG-Motivation in Education; Symposium
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Beaudry B; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Iterating Towards Success: Detailing the Developmental Process of an Observational Manual for Teachers’ Motivational Supports. *Jessica Hunter, McGill University; Cole D. Johnson, McGill University; Marianne Dubé, McGill University; Sydney Perkins, McGill University; Natasha De Cotiis, McGill University; Lucas Frankel, McGill University; Romane Monnet, McGill University; Johana Sava, McGill University; Shubhangi Bhardwaj, McGill University; Sanheeta Shankar, McGill University; Tal Sterling-Eilok, McGill University; Jing Lin, McGill University; Kristy A. Robinson, McGill University; Florence Lessard, McGill University*

Uncovering Cultural Blind Spots: Divergences in Human vs. AI Interpretations of Culturally Responsive Mathematics Pedagogy. *Jingyun Wu, Indiana University; Jamaal*

Matthews, University of Michigan

Applications of Critical Classroom Video Analysis and Natural Language Processing to Observe Student Engagement in Classroom Discourse. *Christine Lee Bae, Virginia Commonwealth University; Kamil Hankour, Virginia Commonwealth University; Kimberly Williamson, Lehigh University; Morgan Les DeBusk-Lane, Gallup; Rachel Niemira, Virginia Commonwealth University; Ryan LeVault, Virginia Commonwealth University; Singith Nuwanga Perera, Virginia Commonwealth University; Gabriella Osei-Poku, Virginia Commonwealth University*

Using Observational Data to Analyze Motivationally Supportive Instruction and Culturally Responsive and Sustaining Pedagogies. *Adriana I. Martinez Calvit, University of Missouri - St. Louis; Haeun Park, The Ohio State University; Tzu-Jung Lin, The Ohio State University; Eric M. Anderman, The Ohio State University*

Chairs: *Jessica Hunter, McGill University; Haeun Park, The Ohio State University*

Discussant: *Toni Kempler Rogat, Purdue University*

57.058. Building Coalitions of Solidarity: Humanizing Praxis, Indigenous Epistemologies and Education for Transformation. SIG-Paulo Freire; Symposium Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Los Feliz; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Towards Interconnectedness: African Indigenous Knowledge Systems as fertile ground for collective knowing and resistance. *Charlotte Achieng-Evensen, Chapman University*
Building Abolitionist Networks of Care: Lessons in Mutual Aid & Community Political Education Work. *Ndindi Kitonga, Angeles Workshop School*

Challenging Fascism with the “Revolutionary Reason and Force” of Black and Latinx Communities: Building Solidarity and Collective Action. *Lilia D. Monzo, Chapman University; Brittne Ferguson, Chapman University*

“Somos Mujeres Empoderadas”: Building Solidarity and Collective Leadership Among Immigrant Mothers in the Schools. *Jenny Zavala, Chapman University*

Chair: *Lilia D. Monzo, Chapman University*

Discussant: *Suzanne SooHoo, Chapman University*

57.059. Queer and Trans International and Global Perspectives in Education: Oral Histories and Policy Analysis. SIG-Queer Studies; Paper Session Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Beaudry A; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Global Perspectives on Transgender Inclusion: A Critical Policy Analysis and Comparative Case Study. *Benjamin C. Kennedy, University of California - San Diego*

Lived Realities, Cross-National Perspective: USA Educators’ LGBTQ2S+ Oral Histories and Norwegian Students’ Understanding of LGBTQ2S+-ness. *Michael Bartone, Central Connecticut State University; Jon Martin Larsen,*

Kristiania University

Ruler-skirts, Rights-kites and Rainbow Ribbons: making gender equality matter with pre-teens in arts-activist research. *EJ Renold, Cardiff University*

Risk and Uncertainty: The High Stakes of International Relocation for Trans Children Fleeing Anti-trans Policies. *Melinda M. Mangin, Rutgers University*

57.060. Creating Spaces for Parents of Multilingual Children to Showcase Their Expertise and Understanding. SIG-Research in Mathematics Education; Symposium JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum A; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Latine Immigrant Parents’ Conceptualization of Learning and Teaching for Their Children in the U.S. *Kiyomi Sanchez-Suzuki Colegrove, Texas State University; Christian E. Zuniga, University of Texas - Rio Grande Valley; Molly E. McManus, San Francisco State University*

Caregivers as Critical Collaborators: Supporting Culturally Sustaining Mathematics Education. *Beatriz E. Quintos, University of Maryland; Carolina A. Napp-Avelli, University of Maryland; Monica Cardenas Guzman, University of Maryland*

Designing for Family Math: An Equitable Collaboration with Mothers and Teachers at the Elementary Level. *Patricia Fuentes Acevedo, University of California - Irvine; Rossella Santagata, University of California - Irvine*

Making Math Fun: Fostering School-Home Partnerships Between Caregivers and Teachers. *Madeleine Coole, SRI International; Kathleen Jablon Stoehr, Santa Clara University; Sara Rutherford-Quach, SRI Education; Katherine Necochea-Tinco, SRI International; Claudia Rodriguez-Mojica, University of California - Davis; Allison Briceno, San José State University*

Unpacking Caregiver Engagement: A Study of Mexican Mothers’ Experiences in Children’s Mathematics Education. *Fany Salazar, University of Arizona*

Chair: *Cathery Yeh, University of Texas at Austin*

Discussant: *Cathery Yeh, University of Texas at Austin*

57.061. Latina Women in Education. SIG-Research on Women and Education; Paper Session Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304B; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

A Theory of Chicana/Latina Feminist Organizational Change: Examining Racialized and Gendered Experiences of Latina Librarians. *Sally Najera Romero, California State Polytechnic University - Pomona*

Bridging Borders And Barriers: Transforming U.S. Higher Education for International Student Mothers of Color. *Marynes CastilloEspinoza, Pennsylvania State University*

Love Letters as Leadership: Unforgetting Histories and

Imagining Resilient Futures Through Latina Superintendents' Testimonios. *Pinyi Wang, University of Florida; LeAnne C. Salazar Montoya, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Juanita Galaviz, Texas State University; Griselda Vargas, Texas State University; Gina Delgado, UnidoUS; Tracie Trinidad, Aurora Public Schools*

Tamaliza as Methodology: Honoring the Voices and Knowledge of Mujeres in Academic Spaces. *Brenda Rivera, University of Texas - San Antonio; Monica Hernandez, University of Texas - San Antonio; Claudia García-Louis, The University of Texas San Antonio*

Virtual Counterspaces: How Latina Doctoral Students Leverage Social Media to Navigate Academia. *Aide Hernandez, University of Illinois at Chicago; Jennifer Cabrera, University of California - Irvine; Valerie A. Gomez, University of Southern California*

Chair: *LeAnne C. Salazar Montoya, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*

57.062. Reimagining Rural Justice: Critical, Cultural, and Historical Perspectives on Education and Belonging.

SIG-Rural Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum D; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

A Critical Race Nepantlera Methodological Approach to Rural Latinx College Access. *Mayra Puente, University of California - Santa Barbara; Lupita Romo-González, University of California - Santa Barbara; Marlene Lopez Torres, University of California - Santa Barbara; Melissa Romero, University of California - Santa Barbara*

Against Forgetting: Georgia Jeanes Teachers and Educational Liberation in the Red Clay South. *Brittney Kilgore, University of Georgia*

Between Belief and Burnout: The Precarity of Justice Work in Culturally Homogeneous Schools. *Giovanni E. Whyte, University of North Dakota*

It's Clear that Place is Important to Rural People. It's Not Clear Why. *Al Wood, Michigan State University*

Promised Futures, Lived Margins: Rethinking Rural Childhoods in Chinese Boarding Schools. *MANNING LUO, University of Birmingham*

Chair: *Wendy Pfrenger, University of Mississippi*

Discussant: *Erin Gill, University of Pennsylvania*

57.063. Violence Against Educators in Context: New National Evidence from School Personnel Across Roles and Identities. SIG-School Community, Climate, and Culture; Symposium

Westin Bonaventure, Level 2, Echo Park; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

An Examination of Unvictimized Teachers and "What Works" in Secondary Education. *Andrew Holmes Perry, The Ohio State University; Linda Reddy, Rutgers University; Andrew*

Martinez, Center for Court Innovation; Sawyer Hogenkamp, University of California - Los Angeles; Chaoyue Wu, University of California - Los Angeles; Susan D. McMahon, DePaul University; Eric M. Anderman, The Ohio State University; Ron Avi Astor, University of California - Los Angeles; Dorothy L. Espelage, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Frank C. Worrell, University of California - Berkeley

Understanding the Pathway from Violence Against Teacher Turnover: The Mediating Effects of Anxiety and Depression. *Chaoyue Wu, University of California - Los Angeles; Andrew Holmes Perry, The Ohio State University; Linda Reddy, Rutgers University; Andrew Martinez, Center for Court Innovation; Sawyer Hogenkamp, University of California - Los Angeles; Susan D. McMahon, DePaul University; Eric M. Anderman, The Ohio State University; Ron Avi Astor, University of California - Los Angeles; Dorothy L. Espelage, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Frank C. Worrell, University of California - Berkeley*

Student Perpetrated Victimization and Support for School Leadership: Comparing School Staff Roles. *Sawyer Hogenkamp, University of California - Los Angeles; Andrew Holmes Perry, The Ohio State University; Linda Reddy, Rutgers University; Chaoyue Wu, University of California - Los Angeles; Susan D. McMahon, DePaul University; Eric M. Anderman, The Ohio State University; Frank C. Worrell, University of California - Berkeley; Andrew Martinez, Center for Court Innovation; Ron Avi Astor, University of California - Los Angeles; Dorothy L. Espelage, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*

School Psychologists' Perspectives on School Violence: Causes, Consequences, and Recommendations. *Luz Robinson, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Sawyer Hogenkamp, University of California - Los Angeles; Andrew Holmes Perry, The Ohio State University; Susan D. McMahon, DePaul University; Linda Reddy, Rutgers University; Eric M. Anderman, The Ohio State University; Frank C. Worrell, University of California - Berkeley; Andrew Martinez, Center for Court Innovation; Ron Avi Astor, University of California - Los Angeles; Dorothy L. Espelage, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*

Chair: *Linda Reddy, Rutgers University*

Discussant: *Frank C. Worrell, University of California - Berkeley*

57.064. What Was, What's Now, What's Next: University-Based RPP Brokering in Shifting Institutional Contexts.

SIG-School, University, Community Collaborative Research; Symposium
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Los Cerritos; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Emerging Identities: How Context Shapes Early-Stage Research-Practice Partnerships. *Megan E. Welsh, University of California - Davis; Christina Murdoch Mills, University*

of California - Davis; Jarrett Terry, Florida State University; Nicole Patton-Terry, Florida State University

Meeting in the Middle: Navigating RPP Growth, Institutional Complexity, and Sustained Collaboration. *Nina R. Schoonover, University of Virginia; Peter N. Knox, University of Vermont; Jennifer Goldstein, California State University - Fullerton*

Building and Maintaining Sustainable Research Partnerships in a Shifting Sociopolitical Context: Lessons from Long-term RPPs. *Rachel Ruggirello, Washington University in St. Louis; Laura Neergaard Booker, Vanderbilt University; David Bryant Naff, Virginia Commonwealth University*

Chair: *Jennifer Goldstein, California State University - Fullerton*
Discussant: *Paula Arce-Trigatti, National Network of Education Research-Practice Partnerships*

57.065. Negotiating Identity and Pedagogy: Exploring Language Teachers' Roles and Experiences Across Multilingual Education Contexts. SIG-Second Language Research; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum I; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Academic and Ecological Congruence within Dual Language Bilingual Education: A Quasi-Experimental Study of DLBE Teachers. *Trish Morita-Mullaney, Purdue University; Yangyang Zhu, Purdue University; Priya M Dabak, Purdue University; Erica Sponberg, WIDA; Lucia Urena-Rodriguez, Purdue University*

Bridging Readiness and Reality: Exploring Pre-Service Teachers' Preparation to Educate English Language Learners in Southwest Florida. *Burhan Ozfidan, Florida Gulf Coast University; Bruno Halpern, Florida Gulf Coast University*

Multiple Voices, Multiple Languages: A Case Study of a Kindergarten Teacher's Translanguaging and Dialogic Instruction. *Erika Johnson, University of Iowa*

"The reality of teaching is that...we don't get our own classroom": Language teacher identity through intra-action and subjectivity. *Ziqi Li, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Timothy Monreal, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Erin Kearney, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

Chair: *Kellie Rolstad, University of Maryland*
Discussant: *Luis E. Poza, San José State University*

57.066. Broken Links in the Pathway from School to Career. SIG-Sociology of Education; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 501C; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Hidden Advantage along the Pipeline: Wealth and Educational Transitions from High School through Graduate School. *Wesley Jeffrey, University of California - Merced; Christian Michael Smith, University of Georgia; Laura Hamilton,*

University of California - Merced

Internships Beyond Family Connections: How Information Channels with Institutional Support Shape First-Generation Students' Career Development. *Hee Song, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Talent-Effort Discourse in Chinese County-level High School: Social Text, Field Logic and Student Subjectivity. *Yan Huang, Peking University; Ziyue Yang, Peking University*

The Unequal (Mis)Match: Education Field Specificity and Disparities in School-to-Work Linkages. *Ran Liu, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Thao Pham, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Trends in Contextual Effects of School SES on Adolescents' Occupational Expectations: Evidence from PISA 2000–2022 in Korea. *Suyoung Park, The Pennsylvania State University*

Chair: *Eujin Park, Stanford University*

57.067. Reframing Teacher Preparation and Praxis Through Disability, Culture, and Teacher Identity. SIG-Special and Inclusive Education Research; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 3; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Lives of Neurodivergent Teachers. *Ilene Ivins, Alder Graduate School of Education; Cindy Parks, University of California - Davis; Laurel E. Towers, University of California - Davis; Lauren Lindstrom, University of California - Davis*

Examining Global Discourses of Dis/Ability and Race in Teacher Praxis Research. *Nahid Husain-Habib, University of Illinois Chicago; David I. Hernandez-Saca, University of Northern Iowa; Dona Dinithi Ferdinando, University of Northern Iowa*

Unprepared and Overwhelmed: Gaps in Teachers' Self-Efficacy for Multilingual learners with Disabilities. *Jocelyn Belden, Georgia State University*

Preparing for Inclusive Futures: Reimagining Special Education Teacher Preparation with Culturally and Linguistically Responsive Tools. *Cametreus Clardy, University of Florida*

Unforgetting Disability Histories: Mapping Teachers' Professional Histories for Historical Consciousness. *Marie Wagner, Rockhurst University*

57.068. Advances in Multilevel Modeling for Complex Data and Study Designs. SIG-Structural Equation Modeling and Multilevel Modeling Methods; Paper Session
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Echo Park; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Comparing Traditional Models and Random Intercept Models in Longitudinal Mediation. *Qiyue Zhang, Texas A&M University; Paul R. Hernandez, Texas A&M University; Oiman Kwok, Texas A&M University; Wen Luo, Texas A&M University; Karen E. Rambo-Hernandez, Texas A&M University*

Designing Multisite Randomized Trials to Detect (Conditional) Indirect Effects. *Fangxing Bai, Montana State University; Benjamin Kelcey, University of Cincinnati; Amota Ataneka, University of Cincinnati; Yanli Xie, Florida State University; Kyle T. Cox, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Nianbo Dong, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*

Sampling and Measurement Error Impacts on the Estimation of L2 X-Y Relationships in MLMs. *Timothy R. Konold, University of Virginia; Elizabeth A. Sanders, University of Washington*

Towards Robust Prediction and Classification of Cluster-Specific Effects in Hierarchical Linear Modeling. *Graham Ward Buhrman, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Jee-Seon Kim, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Chair: *Haoran Li, University of Minnesota*

57.069. Perspectives on Early Childhood and K–12 Learning. SIG-Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis; Paper Session InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 6th Floor, Broadway; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Disinvestment by Design: A Systematic Review of Child Care Deserts and Early Childhood Access in Marginalized Communities. *Eboni N. Bango, Texas A&M University; Jemimah L Young, Texas A&M University*

Identification of STEM Talent A Systematic Review Focusing on K-12 Gifted Education.pdf. *Jiaqi Tang, Tsinghua University; Huichao Bi, Tsinghua University*

Learning Supports in pre-K-12 Digital Learning Games: A Systematic Review of the Literature. *Seyedahmad Rahimi, University of Florida; Salah Esmailigoujar, University of Florida; Mahboobeh Mehrvarz, Carnegie Mellon University; Samaneh Abdoli, Farhangian University; Bruce McLaren, Carnegie Mellon University*

The Effects of Early Childhood Science Educational Interventions on Children's Science Achievement: A Meta-Analysis. *Kathleen Lynch, University of Connecticut; Catherine Armstrong Asher, University of Michigan; Amelia Wenk Gotwals, Michigan State University; John Settlege, University of Connecticut*

57.070. Language and Literacy Development and Decolonization through AI and Robotics. SIG-Technology as an Agent of Change in Teaching and Learning; Paper Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum J; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Empowering Linguistically Responsive Teachers with Text-to-Video Generative AI as a Multimodal Intelligent Classroom Assistant. *Matthew Nyaaba, University of Georgia; SungEun Min, Kutztown University of Pennsylvania; Gayoung Choi, University of Nebraska - Lincoln*

Robot-Mediated Interactive Read-Alouds: Supports and

Barriers for Young Children's Literacy Development. *Iman Bakhoda, HighScope Educational Research Foundation; Pourya Shahverdi, Oakland University; Katie Rousso, University of Michigan; Evan Dallas, Oakland University; Wing-Yue Geoffrey Louie, Oakland University*

Reclaiming Voice through AI: A Phenomenological Inquiry into Language Decolonization among Arab Bilingual Writers. *Maha Alhabbash, United Arab Emirates University; Najah Al Mohammedi, United Arab Emirates University; Hana Omar, United Arab Emirates University; Safa Al Othali, ADEK*

Chair: *Matthew Nyaaba, University of Georgia*

Discussant: *Ching Sing Chai, Chinese University of Hong Kong*

57.071. Part 1: Celebrating the 60th Anniversary of Urban Education: Past, Present, and Future Directions. SIG-Urban Learning, Teaching, and Research; Symposium JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum C; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Urban and Suburban Children's Performance on the Naglieri Verbal, Nonverbal and Quantitative General Ability Tests. *Jack Naglieri, George Mason University*

Pinpointing and Profiling Disciplinary Excellence and Exemplary Performance. *John A. Williams, Texas A&M University; Sonyia Richardson, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Chance W. Lewis, University of North Carolina - Charlotte*

Reconceptualizing Verbal Intelligence: Perspectives from Gifted and Talented Black Elementary Students and Teachers in Urban Schools. *Monique Mills, University of Houston; Leslie C. Moore, The Ohio State University; Donna Y. Ford, The Ohio State University*

Acknowledging the Past – Shaping the Present – Informing the Future. *Norma Day-Vines, Johns Hopkins University; Anita A. Young, Johns Hopkins University; Sam Steen, George Mason University*

Civil Rights Violations in Special Education: Eliminating Educational Zones of Resegregation. *Nicholas S. Bell, University of Connecticut; David J. Connor, Hunter College - CUNY*

Black Male Student Scholarship: A Content Analysis of Sixty Years of Urban Education. *Dakota W. Cintron, Cornell University; Monique Nia Golden, University of Connecticut; Paul Singleton, The Potomac School; Desmond A McGlone, George Mason University; Jessica Fort, Virginia Commonwealth University; Colin Byrd, Bowie State University; Erik Hines, George Mason University; James L. Moore, National Science Foundation*

Chair: *Rich Milner, Vanderbilt University*

Discussants: *Donna Y. Ford, The Ohio State University; James L. Moore, National Science Foundation*

Division and SIG Roundtables

57.072. AERA Roundtable Session Friday 1:45 pm; Roundtable Session

57.072-1. How Principal Leadership Practices Influence Teacher Performance (Table 1). Division A - Administration; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Three Types of Headships: Principal Leadership's Impact on ECE Teacher Learning in Teaching Research Groups. *Han QIN, Capital Normal University; Yingying Huang, Chinese University of Hong Kong*

"Will and Skill": How Caring Leadership Triggers Teachers' Behavioral Transformation. *Fei He, Zhejiang International Studies University*

Reimagining Literacy Leadership: Principal Supports for Coaching in the Science of Reading Implementation Efforts. *Beza Tefera Muzein, University of Georgia; Sally J. Zepeda, University of Georgia*

Principal Race and Perceptions of Influence Over the Curriculum. *Thomas Michael Drake, University of Michigan; Sharon Jessica, University of Michigan; Larasati Dwibuana Ayuningtyas, University of Michigan*

Not a job in limbo: Understanding the relationship between assistant principal turnover, teacher turnover, and student attendance. *Seijoon Park, National Institute of Education, Nanyang Technological University, Singapore; Se Woong Lee, University of Missouri*

Chair: *Cynthia Angélica Gallardo, Texas A&M International University*

57.072-2. How Teachers Experience and Perceive Principal Leadership (Table 2). Division A - Administration; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Cultivating a Culture of Growth: How P-12 Leaders Can Foster Teacher Feedback Receptivity. *Caridad Vivian Chrisomalis, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Paternalistic Leadership Behavior and Professional Learning Communities: The Mediating Role of Interpersonal Trust. *Mengxing Zhu, Beijing Normal University; Yonghong Cai, Beijing Normal University; Runjia Tang, Capital Normal University; Yun Qu, Beihang University; Yutian Liu, Beijing Normal University*

Administrator and school support for STEM teaching for all: Teacher perspectives. *Doron Zinger, California State University - Dominguez Hills; Nardos Ghebream, Beyond100K; Frederick Freking, University of Southern*

California

Chair: *Robert White, ECSU*

57.072-3. Curriculum in the Age of AI: Digital Mythopoetics, Media Literacies, and Futurisms (Table 3). Division B - Curriculum Studies; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Digital Mythopoetics and Educational Futures: Archaeological Analysis of AI Image Generation. *Sarah Ishmael, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Spatializing intelligence: Tracing the Curricular Logic of Smartness in Data-driven Educational Infrastructures. *Lucy Zhang, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Toward Generative AI Literacy: Historical Perspectives on Media Literacy Education's Response to Media Technologies. *Xin Chen, University of British Columbia*

57.072-4. Cultural Identity, Race, and Resilience in Counseling (Table 4). Division E - Counseling and Human Development; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Black Male International Student Experiences in Counselor Education: An Exploration of Cultural Assets for Matriculation. *Clarence Bumpas, Old Dominion University; Jordan P. Shannon, Seattle University; Demetrius Cofield, The Ohio State University; Marcus Folkes, Saint Edward's University; Calvin Craig, Duke University*

(Re)Defining Freedom: Prison to University Pathways of Black Scholars through a Counseling Lens. *Lauren Sneed, San Francisco State University*

Understanding and Transforming the Benefits of Affinity Racial Healing Groups. *Stephanie Chang, Stanford University; Farzana Tabitha Saleem Adjah, Stanford University; Won-Fong Lau Johnson, UCLA-Duke National Center for Child Traumatic Stress; Audra Langley, University of California - Los Angeles*

Validating the Impacts of Racism and Microaggressions on BIPOC Youth: The Counselor's Role. *Qiana Spellman, St. John's University; Kelly Kent, Antioch University - Los Angeles*

Chair: *Marlinda Boxley, Bowie State University*

Discussant: *Kerstin Marie Cornell, Baylor University*

57.072-5. Faith, Pedagogy, and Leadership in Catholic Education (Table 5). SIG-Catholic Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Accessing Students' Faith Literacies to Enact Culturally

Relevant Catechesis. *John L. Beltramo, Santa Clara University*

Beyond Saints and Statues: A Critical Examination of Faith Formation in Catholic Schools. *Courtney O'Grady, University of Alabama; Kevin J. Burke, University of Georgia; John Reyes, Boston College; Jonathon E. Sawyer, University of Colorado - Boulder; Kathleen M. Sellers, Duke University; Andrew F. Miller, Boston College*

Conceptualizing Religious and Spiritual Meaning-Making in Teacher Education: Broadening Visions of Vocation and Educator Formation. *Katherine M. Ward, Michigan State University*

Examining the Influence of Collaboration on Catholic School Leaders' Pursuit of Instructional and Organizational Change. *Andrew F. Miller, Boston College; Michael T. O'Connor, Boston College; Whitney M. Hegseth, University of La Verne; Andrew Hurley, Boston College*

Revisiting the Catholic School Advantage: Evidence from Before and Since the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Wei Gao, Boston College; Shaun Dougherty, Boston College; Myra Rosen-Reynoso, Boston College; Charles T. Cownie, Boston College*

Chair: *Antonio Felix, Loyola Marymount University*

57.072-6. Instructional & Professional Learning Leadership (Table 6). SIG-Learning and Teaching in Educational Leadership; Roundtable Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Building Instructional Leadership Capacity through a Virtual Summer Institute for School Leaders. *Beverly J. Irby, Texas A&M University; Hamada Elfarargy, South Dakota State University; Roya Pashmforoosh, Texas A&M University; Rafael Lara-Alecio, Texas A&M University; Fuhui Tong, Texas A&M University*

Experiences and trajectories of Teachers Leading Professional Learning Communities in Chile: Told in the First Person. *Marcela Pena Ruz, Universidad de Chile; Rebecca Ipinza, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Valparaíso; Karen Manríquez, School Pedro Aguirre Cerda; Karla Olea, School Pedro Aguirre Cerda*

Leading for Inclusion: Principals Reimagining Educational Equity Through Networked Improvement Communities. *Meghan E. Cosier, Chapman University; Angelica Munoz, Chapman University; Kari Adams, Chapman University; Audri Sandoval Gomez, Chapman University*

Problem-Solving in Practice: Analyzing Aspiring Leaders' Conversations with Human-Puppeteered Avatar Teachers in Role-Play Simulations. *Secil Caskurlu, Florida State University; Hui Shi, Florida State University; Daniel Moraguez, Florida State University; Seungjie Clarice Han, Florida State University*

57.072-7. Reframing Educational Leadership and Supervision: Integrating Cultural, Organizational, and Instructional Perspectives (Table 7). SIG-Supervision and Instructional Leadership; Roundtable Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Enhancing Practitioner Retention Through the Application of the ABA Clinic Model. *Oscar Silva, National University*
Ethnocultural Leadership as Liberatory Praxis: Ancestral Memory & Cultural Continuity in Global Majority Leaders. *Courtney Wilkerson, Howard University*

Navigating Disorienting Dilemmas: Teacher Candidates' Responses to Deficit Orientations in Clinical Practice. *May H. Lee, Pennsylvania State University*

Discussant: *Megan E. Lynch, Boise State University*

57.072-8. Parenting, Painting, and Puppetry: Innovative Pedagogies for Art Education in a Changing World (Table 8). SIG-Arts and Inquiry in the Visual and Performing Arts in Education; Roundtable Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Bridging Brush and Pixel: A Comparative Study of Traditional and Digital Painting for Pre-Service Art Educators. *Qianyu Zhou, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Puppet Pedagogy: An Inquiry into Animated Educational Objects. *Chris Moffett, Teachers College, Columbia University; Lucius Von Joo, Teachers College, Columbia University; Emmy Semprun, Teachers College, Columbia University; Danielle Tulchinsky, Teachers College, Columbia University; Kevin Klein-Cardena, Teachers College, Columbia University*

When Social Justice Parenting and Teaching Intersect: A Critical Arts-Based Collective Autoethnography. *Ting Fang Chien, Colorado State University; Ran Qi, Weber State University*

Chair: *Catherine Rosamond, School of Visual Arts*

57.072-9. Progressive Education in Practice: Empirical Studies of Dewey Today (Table 9). SIG-Dewey Studies; Roundtable Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Enacting Dewey's Democratic Ideals in K-12 Classrooms. *Kyle Hamilton, University of British Columbia - Okanagan; Margaret A. Macintyre Latta, University of British Columbia - Okanagan*

Past Wisdom, Future Possibilities: Harnessing the Power of Deweyan Educative Aesthetic Experience in Challenging Times. *Rebecca Taylor, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Rearticulating Progressive Education: A Mixed-Methods Study.
Scott Morrison, Elon University; Grace Rasmussen, Elon University

Chair: *Jessica Heybach, Western Michigan University*

57.072-10. Incorporating the Arts into Environmental Education (Table 10). SIG-Environmental Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Bridging the Science of Reading and Environmental Studies: Nature Journaling as an Engaging Pedagogical Strategy.
Lindi Shepard, Johns Hopkins University; Alexis Filippini, Words in the Wild

Planting Futures: Garden-Based STEAM Curriculum for Environmental Awareness and Action. *Katherine Nicole Vela, Utah State University; Kathy Cabe Trundle, Utah State University; Lawrence Krissek, The Ohio State University; Rita A. Hagevik, University of North Carolina - Pembroke; Kaitlin Campbell, University of North Carolina - Pembroke; Aurora Villa, Utah State University; William Boone, Miami University (OH)*

“She’s Gonna Feel Great”: The Intersection of Sustainability Education and Arts Learning in Out-of-School Contexts.
Betsy Maloney Leaf, University of Minnesota; Eric Castle, University of Minnesota - Crookston; Katy Chapman, University of Minnesota - Crookston

Through Documentaries and Films: Geopolitical and Environmental Education on the Amazon Rainforest in Brazil. *Anelise Reich Corseuil, UFSC Universidade Federal de Santa Catarina; Guofang Wan, Loyola University Chicago*

Walking and restorying with plants through stitching with preservice teachers. *Jrene Rahm, University of Montréal*

Chair: *Amelia Lynn King-Kostelac, University of Texas - San Antonio*

Discussant: *Elizabeth Shores, Rowan University*

57.072-11. Religious Identity, Pedagogy, and Lived Practice (Table 11). SIG-Religion and Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Many Ways of Knowing: Pedagogy of Humility Through Islamic Thought. *Muhammad Zulqurnain Ul Haq Qazi, The Ohio State University; Kaha Abdi, The Ohio State University*

“One Heart.” Toward a New Kingdom and a New Korea. *Noël Um-Lo, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Religious Jewish Mothers as Music Mentors and Ethical Curators in the Streaming Era. *Tal Vaizman, The George Washington University; Abigail Wood, University of Haifa; Naomi Cohen Zentner, Bar-Ilan University*

Chair: *Curtis G. Jefferson, University of Washington*

57.073. AERA Roundtable Session Friday 1:45 pm - Gold 1; Roundtable Session

57.073-1. Rapid Waves: Institutions Responses to Shifting Political and Technological Environments (Table 1). Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Bridging Public Perception and Institutional Policy: A Comprehensive Analysis of Artificial Intelligence's Impact on Higher Education. *Chelsea Zhang, University of Pennsylvania; Manuel S. Gonzalez Canche, University of Pennsylvania*

The AI Imperative: A Study of AI Policies for Faculty and Students in U.S. Higher Education. *Yufeng Qian, Louisiana State University*

The Politics of Commencement Speakers: Organizational Contexts of Speech on College Campuses, 1989–2024. *David R. Johnson, Georgia State University; Liang Zhang, New York University*

A Typology of Educational Reform Organizations in Higher Education. *Desiree Zerquera, University of San Francisco*

57.073-2. Listening for Voice: Translanguaging, Identity, and Narrative in Teaching (Table 2). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

“Bright Smile”: A Reflective Narrative of Language Teaching in the Midwest. *Younglong Kim, Oklahoma State University*

Fostering Equity-Based Praxis: Translanguaging-Informed Digital Identity Text Development in Teacher Education. *Chuan Liu, Western University; Julie D'Ippolito, University of Western Ontario; Lihan Wu, Guangxi Minzu University*

Hearing the Voices of Head Start Teachers to Support Emergent Bilinguals Without and With Disabilities. *Jisun Rachel Oh, University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign; Josh Hayes, University of Kansas; Gregory Cheatham, University of Kansas*

Racial Consciousness and Translanguaging: White Monolingual Teachers Navigating Raciolinguistic Criticality in English Literacy Instruction. *Laurie Elisabet Hahn Ganser, University of Minnesota*

Understanding Middle School Science Teachers' Language Ideologies about Translanguaging. *Sissy S. Wong, University of Houston; Yernat Mnuar, university of houston; Jie Zhang, University of Houston*

Chair: *Laurie Elisabet Hahn Ganser, University of Minnesota*

57.073-3. Reflection as Transformation: Preservice Teacher Learning Through Clinical Practice, Simulations, and Technology (Table 3). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

- Looking Back: How Self-Assessment and Reflection Shape Preservice Teachers' Social-Emotional Competency Development. *Rachel Satter, Oregon State University*
- Productive Wobble: Moving Preservice Teachers' Reflection from Description to Application. *Timothy A. Jansky, Eastern Kentucky University; Jason Michael Miller, Eastern Kentucky University*
- Putting Quality over Quantity: The Greater Reflection and Reduced Roster Approach to Clinical Practice. *Kathryn Luet, Rowan University*
- "I Felt Like a Real-Life Teacher": Teacher Candidates Reflect on Development Through Simulations. *Julie Harnett, Syracuse University*
- Lesson Plans as Windows to SRL: Insights from Pre-Service Teachers. *Chen Bitton, Tel Aviv University; Guy Cohen, Tel Aviv University; Anat Cohen, Tel Aviv University*

Chair: *Julie Harnett, Syracuse University*

57.073-4. What Do You Do? Unpacking the Education and Roles of Teacher Educators (Table 4). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

- Developing Non-University-Based Teacher Educators' Researchly Dispositions Through a Collaborative Action Research Community. *Wei Liao, Beijing Normal University; Zhaoxuan Wang, University of Macau; Xiaoyan Li, Beijing Normal University; Qiujiu Dong, Xinjiang Normal University*
- Teacher Educators as Officers: How do teaching-research officers in China leverage administrative authority to support school teachers' professional development. *Yanling Wang, East China Normal University, China; Qiang Fa Ying, East China Normal University*
- The Curricular Knowledge Bases of STEM Teacher Educator Preparation: A Content Analysis. *Brandon M. Butler, Old Dominion University; Stephen Burgin, University of Arkansas at Fayetteville; Nazmun Nahar, Old Dominion University; Natisha Harper, Old Dominion University*
- Unpacking Reflective Practices among Mathematics Teacher Educators: A Preliminary Study. *Helena Loreto Montenegro, Universidad de Chile; Salome Martinez, Universidad de Chile*

Chair: *Ya-Fang Cheng, Western Oregon University*

57.073-5. Implementing Reform, Unraveling Futures: The

Micropolitics and Meaning of Educational Change (Table 5). Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

- Mandatory top-down Reform - Conditions for Effective Implementation. *Nirit Pariente, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev; Dorit Tubin, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev*
- Performativity, Resistance, Commitment, and the Institutional Limitations of Enacting Equity from the Perspectives of Educators in Ontario, Canada: A Critical Policy Analysis. *Shirin Abdmolaei, University of Western Ontario; Goli Rezai-Rashti, Western University*
- The Free Senior High School policy of Ghana broke the first sacred stage of the policy development cycle and, as if that were not enough, it broke all the others. *Lukman Ziblim, Middle East Technical University; Mohammed Ibrahim, Arizona State University*
- The Micropolitics of Implementing a Pay-for-Extra-Duties Initiative: Insights from Principals' Decision-Making Process. *So Ra Yoo, North Carolina State University; Lam D. Pham, North Carolina State University*
- How Do Education Leaders Engage in Data-based Decision-making? The Curious Case of Four-day School Weeks. *J. Cameron Anglum, Lehigh University; Michael Faccinnetto, Southern Lehigh School District; Reina Garcia, Lehigh University; Amanda Abdelaal, Lehigh University; Aaron Park, Saint Louis University*

Chair: *So Ra Yoo, North Carolina State University*

57.073-6. From Crossing to Returning: Teacher Trajectories in Motion (Table 6). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

- Beyond stability: a narrative inquiry into beginning teacher attrition and identity transition in China. *Yarui Chen, Florida State University; Siyuan Chen, College of William & Mary*
- Exploring Intersecting Identities in Language Teacher Development: A Case Study of Three Student-Teachers in Toronto. *Wenyangzi Shi, University of Toronto*
- From "Expatriation" to "Homecoming": Analyzing Factors Influencing Reentry Adaptation of Returnee Academics in Higher Education. *Yitong Jiang, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Jiakuan Lian, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Hongbiao Yin, The Chinese University of Hong Kong*
- International Teacher Identity Negotiation Through Transnational Online Master's Programs: A Narrative Inquiry. *Yueyue Wang, University of Maryland; Wanyi Xie, Peking University*

Chair: *Yarui Chen, Florida State University*

57.073-7. Contemporary Discussions in Learning

Environments 1 (Table 7). SIG-Learning Environments; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

From Recipient to Explorer: How Spatial Learning Environments Enable Active Engagement in Intangible Cultural Heritage Education. *Yuqi Wang, University of Toronto - OISE*
Impact of K-12 Learning Environments on Conceptualizations of Engineering. *Karthigeyan Subramaniam, University of North Texas; Christopher S. Long, University of North Texas; Mila Rosa Librea Carden, University of North Texas*
Perceptions of academic press: Towards understanding why students underperform in reading towards critical thinking. *Nadger Henry, Johns Hopkins University*
The Design of a Field School: Learning Environments with/in a Living Lab. *David B. Zandvliet, Simon Fraser University*
Chair: *Xiangyuan Feng, University of Groningen*

57.073-8. Global Comparisons in Multicultural Education (Table 8). SIG-Multicultural/Multiethnic Education: Theory, Research and Practice; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Cultural Governance and Intergenerational Nurturing Practices in a Paiwan Community: A Care Ethics Perspective. *LIAO YUAN-HSUAN, NATIONAL TAIWAN NORMAL UNIVERSITY*
Examining Chinese International Students' Inquiry Learning: Navigating between Home Cultural Traditions and Western Academic Expectations. *XI (Bridget) WU, Soochow University; Lingshan Li, University of Washington*
Hotspots and Frontiers of International Ethnic Education Research in the Past Decade: A Bibliometric Analysis Based on the SSCI Database (2015-2024). *ZHUO CHEN, Universiti Putra Malaysia*
Multicultural Education Across Borders: A Curricular Analysis of British Columbia, New York State, and South Korea. *Hyeyoung Ghim, University of Missouri - Kansas City; Yeonghwi Ryu, Gwangju National University of Education*
Chair: *Jason Cong Lin, The Education University of Hong Kong*

57.073-9. Banned, Restricted, and Contested: The Politics of Censorship in Education (Table 9). Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Book bans and the Science of Reading: Analyzing literacy education coverage on cable news (2022-2023). *Rachel Skrlac Lo, Villanova University; Thomas Ksiazek, Villanova*

University; Dusy Garcia, Villanova University; Majo James, Villanova University; Gabrielle Girault, Villanova University

Emotional responses of leaders, teachers, and parents from a religious community to a new governmental policy. *Chajim Erlanger, Tel Aviv University; Izhar Oplatka, Tel Aviv University*

State Resistance and Reinforcement: Diverging Paths in (Anti-)Democratic Education Law. *Shophika Vaithyanathasarma, Boston College; Sophie Compston, Boston College; Raquel Muñiz, Boston College*

The Limitation Effect: Experiences of State Policy- Driven Education Restriction in Florida's Public Schools. *Mica Pollock, University of California - San Diego; Hirokazu Yoshikawa, New York University; John Diaz, University of California - San Diego; Abigail Richburg, New York University; Elizabeth Blair Cox, New York University; Andrew Matschiner, Chapman University; Emilie Homan, University of California - San Diego; Abdul-Rehman M. Issa, University of California - San Diego*

The Southern Teacher Narrative: Religion, Education Policy, and Oppositional Parents. *Alexa Muse, University of Oxford*

Chair: *Wesam M. Salem, University of Memphis*

Discussant: *Micah Card, University of California - Santa Cruz*

57.074. AERA Roundtable Session Friday 1:45 pm - Gold 2; Roundtable Session

57.074-1. STEM Pathways and Multicultural Perspectives (Table 1). SIG-Multicultural/Multiethnic Education: Theory, Research and Practice; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Formative Assessment of Multilingual Students in K-12 STEM Education: A Systematic Literature Review. *Bilgehan Ayik, George Mason University; Dai Gu, George Mason University; Woomee Kim, George Mason University; Marjorie H. Haley, George Mason University*

Multicultural Mathematics Education: Does It Matter? A Study of Ethnomathematical Awareness in Preservice Science Teachers. *Wen-Hua Chen, National Taipei University of Education*

Navigating Digital Competence in Multilingual Diverse Classrooms: A Mixed-Methods Study of In-Service Elementary Mainstream Teachers. *Nansia Kyriakou, Frederick University; Nikleia Eteokleous, Frederick University; Maria Mitsiaki, Democritus University of Thrace*

57.074-2. Fostering Care Through Self Study: Caring for Self; Caring for Others (Table 2). SIG-Self-Study of Teacher Education Practices; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Accompanying Teachers: Possibilities for Inspirational Theory, Practice, and Research in Teacher Education. *Ginger Barnhart, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Margaret Ann Donnelly, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*

Exploring Caring Pedagogy Through Self-Study: A Mathematics Educator's Journey. *Kien H. Lim, The University of Texas - El Paso*

Unfolding to Unpack Experiences Through Nature journaling: Arts-based Duoethnography of Two Early Career Academics. *Yun-chen Yen, Pennsylvania State University; Pin-Hsuan Tseng, Pennsylvania State University*

Unforgetting Histories of Marginalizing English Language Learners: Self-Study of Cultivating Holistic Teachers for Inclusive Futures. *Nozomi Inukai, DePaul University*

Chair: *Barbara A. Henderson, San Francisco State University*

57.074-3. Self-Studies Exploring Futures & Opportunities: AI, Equity, and Uncertainty (Table 3). SIG-Self-Study of Teacher Education Practices; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Co-designing Equitable Futures with GenAI and Multilingual Writers: A Collaborative Self-Study. *Weiqiao Zhang, Boston University; Geying Zhang, Boston College; Chuqi Wang, Boston College; Michael Alan Chang, Boston University*

Critical friendship: An Affirming Dialogic Space to Address Uncertain Futures. *Amanda Moody Maestranzi, Lehman College - CUNY; Harriet R. Fayne, Lehman College - CUNY*

Methodological, Technological, and Epistemological Consequences of AI-assisted Teacher Self-studies. *Le Grande Dolino, Indiana University; Bench Go Fabros, Central Luzon State University; Jingyun Wu, Indiana University; Esther Kataate Namakula, Indiana University*

Navigating Resistance and Responding to Opportunity as Dean: A Self-Study of Teacher Education Leadership. *Diane Yendol-Hoppey, University of North Florida; Brandon M. Butler, Old Dominion University*

Chair: *Charity M. Dacey, Touro University*

57.074-4. Shaping Graduate Success: Relationships, Writing, & Institutional Culture (Table 4). SIG-Graduate and Postdoctoral Education across the Disciplines; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

A Critical Policy Discourse Analysis of Language Usage in PhD Departmental Handbooks. *Joy Nwannediya Emmanuel, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Aireale J. Rodgers, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Brian A. Burt, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Xiaohan Liu, University of*

Wisconsin - Madison

Practitioner Pathways to Justice-Oriented Leadership: Exploring Collaboration and Community in Three CPED-Influenced EdD Programs. *Jill Alexa Perry, Carnegie Project on the Education Doctorate; Elizabeth C. Reilly, California State University - Channel Islands; Kathleen Kelly Wallace, Sacred Heart University*

Reciprocal Care in Graduate Advising: Understanding Latine Doctoral Students' Experiences through The Model of Wholeness in Graduate Advising (MWGA). *Yuriko Sato, University of Wisconsin-Madison; Mark R. Moralez, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Jorge L Rivera-Colón, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

The Prestige Paradox: How Status Structures Access to Graduate Education. *Steve Desir, University of Southern California*

57.074-5. Identity, Culture and Sustaining Language (Table 5). SIG-Bilingual Education Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Black Girl Multilinguals: A Linguistic Exploration of their Languagefulness. *Reka C. Barton, University of Maryland*
Chinese Immigrant Descendent Children's Experience of Home Biliteracy in the U.S. *Qinghua Liu, Boston College*

Exploring the Bilingual Journeys of Three Children through Translanguaging Practices in a Heritage Language Classroom. *Kyungjin Hwang, University of South Carolina*
More Than Words: Chinese Immigrant Parents' Heritage Language Strategies Amid Identity and Change. *Yige Zou, University of Washington*

Negotiating Identity in a Translanguaging Learning Space: A Case Study of Young Chinese American Children. *Zhen Valerie Ren, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

57.074-6. Language Pedagogies Across the Content Areas (Table 6). SIG-Bilingual Education Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Audio Effect on Young Learners' Multimodal Reading Comprehension and Processing: L1-L2 Eye-tracking Comparison Study. *Yiwen Sun, Hong Kong Polytechnic University; Nuo Li, The Hong Kong Polytechnic University; Xinhua Zhu, Hong Kong Polytechnic University; Yi Guan, Hong Kong Polytechnic University*

Bilingual Students' and Teachers' Perspectives on STEM Literacies. *Yang Wang, University of South Carolina; Jing Zhang, University of South Carolina; Shuang Du, University of South Carolina*

Creating a Multilingual English Language Arts Classroom: Exploring Practical Approaches for PreK-12. *Mandy*

Stewart, Texas Woman's University

Examining Home Language Input and Cross-Language Oral Language Skills in PreK Spanish-English DLLs. *Shaunacy Robert Sutter, University of South Florida; Lisa M. Lopez, University of South Florida; Charles E. Flowers, California State University - Fullerton*

Exploring Explicit Analogical Reasoning in Second Language Acquisition: Insights for L2 Scaffolding. *Liantao Shan, University of California - Merced; Zenaida Aguirre-Munoz, University of California - Merced; Tyler Marghetis, University of California - Merced*

57.074-7. Preparing Teachers to Revisit and Respond to the Linguistic Landscape (Table 7). SIG-Bilingual Education Research; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Unforgetting the Past, Envisioning Tomorrow: Rebuilding Bilingual Teacher Pathways for a Multilingual California. *Nirmla Griarte Flores, California State Polytechnic University - Pomona; Clara Amador-Lankster, National University; Adam Sawyer, California State University - Bakersfield; Eduardo Rafael Munoz-Munoz, San José State University; Danna Moreno, UC Santa Cruz*

Using Photovoice to Explore Pre-service Teachers' Understanding of Linguistically Responsive Practices for Emergent Bilingual Children. *Hae Min Yu, Lewis University*

Whose Bilingualism Counts? Latina Teachers, Border Crossings, and Language Ideologies. *Tipsuda Chaomuangkhong, Arizona State University; Cory Alan Buckband, Arizona State University*

57.074-8. Mentorship, Antiracism, and Fugitive Literacies in Youth Justice Work (Table 8). SIG-Critical Educators for Social Justice; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Antiracism Socialization and School-Level Political Engagement of Adolescents: The Influence of Teachers, Peers, and Families. *Emily Maurin-Waters, University of California - Los Angeles; M. Alejandra Arce, University of California - Riverside; Jada Cheek, University of California - Santa Cruz; Christopher Wegemer, University of California - Los Angeles; Laura Wray-Lake, University of California - Los Angeles; Elan Hope, Policy Research Associates*

Educational cultural visionaries: how BlackQueer adults mentor, embrace, and love on BlackQueer youth. *Javania Michelle Webb, Independent Scholar*

Transformational Mentorship and Radical Storytelling: Reproductive Justice for and by Pregnant and Parenting Youth. *Laura Ruth Johnson, Northern Illinois University*

Unforgetting and Reimagining: Fugitive Literacies in a Youth Social Justice Collective. *Christina Salazar, Texas Woman's University*

"Here, Everyone's Voice Matters": Grassroots Justice, Belonging, and Pluriversal Futures in Café Without Borders. *Lamiaa Mohamed Fathy Eid, University of Massachusetts - Amherst*

Chair: *Laura Fittz Parks, Fort Lewis College*

57.074-9. Navigating Tension and Transformation: Preparing Teachers for Justice in a Divided World (Table 9). SIG-Critical Educators for Social Justice; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Analyzing Picture Books with Black Language for Transformational Teacher and Student Learning. *Natasha A. Thornton, Spelman College*

Co-Constructing Supports for Justice-Oriented Early Career Teachers. *Katie Harlan Eller, Marist University; Kathleen Van Cauwenberge, Marist College; Amanda Williamson, Marist College*

Coming Together in Conflicted Times: Making Sense of the Sociopolitical Landscape in a PLC. *Jennifer Ervin, University of Wisconsin - Eau Claire*

"I'm not worried if I'm getting in trouble": How Middle Grades Teacher Candidates Imagine Social Justice Teaching. *Samantha Leihsing, University of Texas - San Antonio*

Untangling words from work: Teacher residents take up Rural Educational Justice in era of polycrisis. *Christy Howard, East Carolina University; Angela Novak, East Carolina University; Jennifer L. Gallagher, East Carolina University*

Chair: *Shawn S. Savage, University of North Carolina - Wilmington*

57.075. AER Roundtable Session Friday 1:45 pm - Gold 3; Roundtable Session

57.075-1. Resilience and Renewal: Efficacy, Ethics, and Leadership Post-Pandemic (Table 1). SIG-Stress, Coping, and Resilience; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Dynamic Trajectories of Academic Resilience: A Longitudinal Study in the Chinese Context. *Tianxue Cui, Dalian Maritime University; Mucheng Zhang, Beijing Normal University; QIMENG LIU, Beijing Normal University*

From Goal Beliefs to Ethical Practice: Exploring the Mediating Role of Moral Resilience in Teachers' Moral Awareness. *Shu-Jyun Liou, National Sun Yat-sen University; Chih Ting Chang, National Sun Yat-sen University; Shu Ching Yang, National Sun Yat-sen University*

Rebounding Efficacy, Enduring Burnout: Teachers' Needs in a

Post-Pandemic Education System. *Alicia Brands, Notre Dame of Maryland University*

The Hazardous Influence of Mental Health on School Principals' Leadership Self-Efficacy and Sustainability. *Eleanor Su-Keene, Texas A&M University; Jenna Doane, The University of New Mexico; John O. Ajamobe, Texas A&M University*

Thriving After Crisis: Mixed-Method Research on Teacher Resilience Post-COVID-19. *Tim Buttler, Burman University*

Chair: *Vanessa Hammler Kenon, University of Texas - San Antonio*

57.075-2. Crisis as a Catalyst in International Education

(Table 2). SIG-International Studies; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Educational Leadership in Wartime Lebanon: Responding to Crisis with Resilience and Adaptability. *Julia Mahfouz, University of Colorado - Denver; Rana Ziad Bassaj, University of Colorado - Denver*

Beyond Words, Across Borders: A Pictorial SES Instrument Validated for Diverse Global Contexts. *Boshi Wang, Georgia State University; Audrey J. Leroux, Georgia Institute of Technology; Niyati Malhotra, World Bank; Tomas Koustecky, World Bank; Stephanie Gottwald, Curious Learning; Tinsley Galyean, Curious Learning*

Language Policy and Planning in Iraqi Education: A Century of Crisis (1920–Present). *Hadi Pir, Yazda*

Teachers' Well-Being During the Finnish Two-Year Pre-Primary Education Trial: Negative, Positive, and Neutral Experiences in Relation to Burnout and Work Engagement. *Heli Johanna Muhonen, University of Jyväskylä; Hilla Villanen, University of Jyväskylä; Maarit Alasuutari, University of Jyväskylä; Marja-Kristiina Lerkanen, University of Jyväskylä*

Chair: *Dion Burns, Learning Policy Institute*

57.075-3. Critical Issues in Contemporary Education Across Nations (Table 3). SIG-International Studies; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Factors Associated with Persistence in STEM: The Case of Undergraduate Women in Ethiopian Universities. *Meseret F. Hailu, University of Georgia; So Yoon Yoon, University of Cincinnati; Qin Xie, University of Minnesota*

Second generation Sub-Saharan African youth: Parental and family influences on post-secondary educational achievement in Canada. *Alana C. Butler, Queen's University - Kingston*

Beliefs and Practices of Selected Effective Private School Teachers in Mumbai, India. *Swathi Menon, College of*

William & Mary; Leslie W. Grant, College of William & Mary; James H. Stronge, College of William & Mary

Challenges in Cross-national Framework Curriculum Transfer: The Case of China's Undergraduate Vocational Education.

Jia Li, The Education University of Hong Kong

Chair: *Eman Abo-Zaed Arar, Texas State University*

57.075-4. Inclusion, Transnationalism, and Pedagogical Innovation in Africa and the Caribbean (Table 4). SIG-Caribbean and African Studies in Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Building and Bridging Across Borders: An HBCU-Community-Based Partnership to Expand STEM Access through the Ventaja Panamá Study Abroad Program. *Beverly A. King Miller, Prairie View A&M University; Kay Coates, Georgia Southern University; Myltazaire Crayton, Prairie View A&M University; Douglas M. Butler, Prairie View A&M University; Nina Cooper, University of New Mexico*

Community and Not Identity First: How Bahamian Teachers Educate Students with Disabilities Without a Formal Inclusion Model. *Phillandra Samantha Smith, University of Pittsburgh; Jaleah N Robinson, Duquesne University*

Teacher Instructional Practices and School Readiness in ECE Classrooms in Ethiopia: Pilot Study Results. *Kassa Michael, Addis Ababa University; Ann A. O'Connell, Rutgers University; Winifred Wilberforce, The Ohio State University; Mulugeta W/Michael, Addis Ababa University; Fiseha Teklu, Addis Ababa University; Meseret Teshome, Addis Ababa University; Jackie Goodway, Michigan State University; Arya Ansari, The Ohio State University; Laura M. Justice, The Ohio State University*

Through the Eyes of Caribbean Immigrants: Reimagining Our Future with Children's Picture Books. *Natakki Jones, University of Rhode Island*

Chair: *Jawanza Kalonji Rand, Teachers College, Columbia University*

57.075-5. Pushing the Dialogue on Equity, Inclusion, and Justice in Educational Change (Table 5). SIG-Educational Change; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

"Taking Our Rights Away": The Impact of Book Bans on Queer and Trans Students. *Sonny Partola, University of Wisconsin - Stevens Point; Nicole C. Wilson Steffes, University of Utah & Westminster University; Rosie Ojeda, California Polytechnic State University - San Luis Obispo*

Bringing a Missing Diversity Into School: Introduction of the Neurodiversity-Informed Culturally Responsive Framework. *Hoi Kiu Karis Tao, The Chinese University of Hong Kong;*

Gary Lam, The Chinese University of Hong Kong

Good for some, not all: English-only and language immersion teachers' perceptions of implementing SoR-informed curriculum. *Letitia Basford, Hamline University; Annie C. Ittner, Hamline University*

Internationalisation with Chinese Characteristics: Exploring the Paradox in Students' Experiences at International Branch Campuses. *Mei Lai, The University of Hong Kong*

Chair: *Sonny Partola, University of Wisconsin - Stevens Point*

57.075-6. Imagining a future of belonging and community-centered instruction through high school redesign (Table 6). SIG-Innovative School Transformation and Reform;

Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Making Magic out of a Mandate: From Consolidation to Robust Redesign. *Charlotte Thompson, Learning Policy Institute*

Remodeling mindsets: leveraging instructional innovation toward systemwide change. *Josette Neal-de-Stanton, Envision Learning Partners*

Educating alongside: student identity as a multiplier of challenging and community-engaged learning. *Chela Myesha Delgado, University of California - Berkeley*

Chair: *Isaiah Moore, University of Kentucky*

Discussant: *Cheryl E. Jones-Walker, Learning Policy Institute*

57.075-7. The Future Of Research-Informed Education? Building Societies Resilient To Misinformation And Polarization (Table 7). SIG-Research Use; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Conceptualizing The Ideas-Informed Society. *Chris Brown, University of Southampton*

Who Benefits From Ideas Engagement? Findings From A Seven-Country Study. *Ruth Luzmore, University of Southampton*

Tackling Misinformation: Implications For Education. *Yin Wang, University of Southampton - Highfield*

Chair: *Stephen W. MacGregor, University of Calgary*

Discussant: *Jonathan A. Supovitz, University of Pennsylvania*

57.075-8. Exploring Social Emotional Learning in Higher Education (Table 8). SIG-Social and Emotional Learning; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

AI and social learning: A study of preservice teacher perceptions. *Qing Li, Towson University; Michael Colin Levi, Towson University; Emily Bailey, Towson University;*

Ruddhi Wadadekar, Maryland Fire and Rescue Institute

Art and Science of Flourishing for College Students: A Mixed-methods Study of Instructors' Experiences. *Vani Gupta, Pennsylvania State University; Rachel Murray, Pennsylvania State University; Laura Evans, Pennsylvania State University; Robert William Roeser, Pennsylvania State University*

Unpacking Social-Emotional Learning in Teacher Education: A Systematic Review of Research and Practice. *Yanbei Chen, Syracuse University; Jing Lei, Syracuse University; Shiqin Wu, Shanghai Pudong Institute of Education Development, China*

Chair: *Cynthia M. Sistek, National University*

57.075-9. Factors Influencing Development of Social Emotional Learning in Youth (Table 9). SIG-Social and Emotional Learning; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Balanced or Not? —Latent Profiles of Students' Social-Emotional Skills During the Middle-to-High School Transition. *Hansheng Zhang, East China Normal University; Jing Zhang, East China Normal University; Lijuan Hu, East China Normal University*

Students display five distinct social-emotional skill profiles: A person-centered analysis. *Jianhua Zhang, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Faming Wang, Zhejiang University; Ronnel B. King, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Xiaoyao Liu, Chinese University of Hong Kong*

Teachers' use and perceptions of SEL Kernels in afterschool settings. *Stephanie M. Jones, Harvard University; Rebecca Bailey, Harvard University; Hannah Broderick, Harvard University; Janina Eberhart, Harvard University; Sarah Farnsworth Hatch, Harvard University; Lillian Massaro, Harvard University; Bryan Nelson, Harvard University; Laura Stickle, Harvard University; Chelsea Rubin, Harvard University*

Transformative Social and Emotional Learning in a Youth Mental Health Advocacy Committee. *Rebecca S. Levine, University of California - San Diego*

Social and Emotional Competencies as Gendered Moderators of Bullying Victim-Perpetrator Link: Evidence from Chinese Youth. *Xuan Wang, University of Hong Kong; Juyeon Lee, The University of Hong Kong*

Chair: *Aakash Arvind Chowkase, Yale University*

57.076. AER Roundtable Session Friday 1:45 pm - Gold 4; Roundtable Session

57.076-1. Learning Through Uncertainty: Curiosity, Emotion, and Creativity in Science Education (Table 1). Division C - Learning and Instruction; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;

1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

- Design and validation of a conceptual model for students' scientific literacy. *Cuixin Li, Beijing Normal University; Yang Yang, Beijing Normal University; Yafeng Zheng, Beijing Normal University*
- Exploring how Disposition toward Scientific Uncertainty Navigation and Epistemic Curiosity Interact to Influence Learning Engagement. *Bukola Omowumi Akinbadewa, Arizona State University; Ying-Chih Chen, Arizona State University; Michelle Jordan, Arizona State University; Jongchan Park, Arizona State University; Carlos Meza-Torres, Arizona State University; Chin-Chung Tsai, National Taiwan Normal University*
- Middle School Students' Learning Engagement and Achievement in an Uncertainty-driven Science Classroom. *Yu Ye, Arizona State University; Carlos Meza-Torres, Arizona State University; Jongchan Park, Arizona State University; Ying-Chih Chen, Arizona State University; Michelle Jordan, Arizona State University*
- Roles of Grain Size and Emotions in Conceptual Change When Reading Different Refutation Texts. *Victoria Teed, Washington State University; Onur Ramazan, University of Hong Kong; Gan Jin, Washington State University; Adam Ulysess Coldiron, Washington State University; Robert W. Danielson, Washington State University - Spokane*

57.076-2. Using AI to Learn in Multi-lingual Contexts (Table 2). Division C - Learning and Instruction Cosponsored with Division C - Learning and Instruction; Roundtable Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

- Exploring the Role of AI in Enhancing EFL Students' Academic Writing and Self-Regulated Learning. *Azzah Alzahrani, University at Buffalo - SUNY*
- Human-AI Collaborative Feedback Enhances EFL Writing with Chain-of-Thought Prompting under SFL Guidance. *Jialing Wu, East China Normal University; Huirong Gao, East China Normal University*
- Integrating AI Literacy into Math Education: A Study on AI Self-Efficacy and Math Motivation. *Linlin Li, WestEd; Jie Chao, The Concord Consortium; Trudi Lord, Concord Consortium; Rebecca Ellis, The Concord Consortium; Kelly Collins, WestEd; Wanli Xing, University of Florida; yuanlin zhang, Texas Tech University; April Fleetwood, Florida Virtual School*
- Reframing AI as Amplifier: Disciplinary Logics and Learner Agency in EFL Academic Reading. *Xiaohang Luo, University of Pennsylvania; Yingqi Wang, University of Hong Kong*

Chair: *Zhaochen Gu, University of Illinois at Chicago*

57.076-3. Rethinking the Role of Learning Spaces (Table 3).

Division C - Learning and Instruction; Roundtable Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

- From Stage to Space: Teacher Roles, Instructional Strategies, and Self-Regulated Learning in Flexible Learning Spaces. *Orit Avdiel, The Open University of Israel; Ina Blau, The Open University of Israel*
- How Academic Performance Shapes Place Attachment of Primary School Students? A Chinese Qualitative Case Study. *Jiamin Cheng, East China Normal University; Yijun Wu, East China Normal University; Yuxi Xia, East China Normal University*
- Reimagining Learning Spaces: Examining Adjustments to Learning Environments Across Two Trump Administrations. *Kristina M. Stamatis, University of Nebraska Omaha; James Dosky, Cherry Creek Schools*
- Reimagining the Future Classroom: Understanding Student Reproductions of Traditional Learning Spaces Despite Unlimited Imagination Prompts. *Elif Ozturk, Middle East Technical University; Nur Cakir, Middle East Technical University; Serap Sevimli Çelik, Edith Cowan University*
- Chair: *Charles E. Flowers, California State University - Fullerton*

57.076-4. Innovations in Item Response Theory for Modeling Student Performance and Growth (Table 4). Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Roundtable Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

- A Comparison of Combined Scoring and Standard-setting approaches applied to an Interim Assessment in Predicting Statewide Assessment Performance. *Michelle Paul, Orange County Public School; Stephen A. Sivo, University of Central Florida; Parul Acharya, Columbus State University*
- Evaluating Longitudinal Change in STEM Identity: Explanatory Rasch Modeling. *Justice Dadzie, University of Alabama; Daniel O. Oyeniran, University of Alabama; Joni M. Lakin, University of Alabama*
- Examining the Latent Structure of Self-Reported Constructs to Enhance STEM Program Evaluation. *Theode Niyirinda, University of Alabama; Joni M. Lakin, University of Alabama; Daniel O. Oyeniran, University of Alabama*
- Second Order Latent Growth Modeling in Ordinal Responses : Focusing on Model Specification and Evaluation. *Sook Hyun Park, University of Texas at Austin; Tiffany A. Whittaker, University of Texas at Austin*
- Using Dynamic Item Response Theory to Model Ability Development in Online Learning. *Alice Xu, University of California - Los Angeles; Zhihua Ma, Shenzhen University; Guanyu Hu, Michigan State University; Icy Yunyi Zhang, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

57.076-5. Designing for Self-Regulation: AI, Scaffolding, and Learner Agency (Table 5). Division C - Learning and Instruction; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

From Cognitive Load to Co-Adaptive Scaffolding: A Design-Based Inquiry of an AI Learning Tool. *Hongming Li, University of Florida; Salah Esmailigoujar, University of Florida; Hai Li, University of Florida; Nazanin Adhami, University of Florida; Rui Tammy Huang, University of Florida*

Integrating Self-Regulated Learning in Generative AI Chatbots: A Quasi-Experimental Study in Programming Education. *Wei-Chih Hsu, National Yang Ming Chiao Tung University; Jerry Chih-Yuan Sun, National Yang Ming Chiao Tung University*

Motivational Effects of Virtual Field Trips. *Bernhard M. Ertl, Universität der Bundeswehr München; Kerstin Bohlen, Universität der Bundeswehr München*

Teachers in Transition: Ecosystemic Perspectives on SRL Support Attitudes and Behaviors Post-Pandemic. *Shuyi Chen, Zhejiang University; Jing Wang, Zhejiang University*

Understanding and Fostering Curiosity and Self-Motivation in Digital Environments. *Farhan Ali, Nanyang Technological University - National Institute of Education*

Chair: *Daryn Dever, University of Florida*

57.076-6. Human-AI Collaboration and Dialogic Learning

(Table 6). Division C - Learning and Instruction; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Discussing Exemplars with GenAI or Peers: The Role of Self-regulated Learning Strategies. *Jiahe Gu, The Education University of Hong Kong; Dan SUN, The Education University of Hong Kong; Zi Yan, The Education University of Hong Kong*

Examining the Effectiveness of LLMs as Online Teaching Assistants for Students through Cognitive Presence. *Arjun Rawal, North Carolina School of Science and Mathematics; Harrish Ayyanar Jeyajothi Pommiraj, University College London - IOE; Yuyang Tong, Stanford University; Rohit Sandadi, University of California - Berkeley; Taransh Goyal, McMaster University; Charith Narreddy, Georgia Institute of Technology; Ishaan Gangwani, Indus International School*

Interact More, Learn More? A Randomized Controlled Trial of GenAI Tutors on Student Learning. *Weijiao Huang, University of Hong Kong; Andrew Thoeni, University of North Florida; Luke K. Fryer, University of Hong Kong*

Role-Based Generative AI for Equitable Formative Feedback: Mixed-Methods Evidence from a Web-Based Course.

Chenyu Zhang, Massachusetts Institute of Technology; Xiaohang Luo, University of Pennsylvania

The Battle of Wits: Comparing Single-Agent System and Multi-Agent Debate System in Scaffolding Argumentative Writing. *Lin Dai, East China Normal University; Jing Leng, East China Normal University*

Chair: *Anastasia L. Betts, Learnology Labs*

57.076-7. Reimagining Introductory Statistics: A Research-Practice Partnership Model for Impactful Statistics Education (Table 7). SIG-Educational Statisticians;

Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Fostering Transfer in Intro Stats: A Modeling-First Curriculum Grounded in Practicing Connections Pedagogy. *Caylor Davis, CourseKata; Mariela Rivas, University of California - Los Angeles*

Integrating R Programming into Introductory Statistics: College Students' Perceptions of and Attitudes Towards R. *Matthew Jackson; Jisun Min, Yonsei University; Claudia C. Sutter, CourseKata*

From Invisible Problems to Instructional Change: Teacher-Led Innovation through Teaching Improvement Groups (TIGs). *Ji Son, California State University - Los Angeles; Karen Aguilar, Patrick Henry High; Renee Hill, Morse High; Sarah Gale, Lehi High; Tyler Haslam, Granger High; Jennifer Knapp, Mission Bay High; Pamela Patterson, La Jolla Country Day School; Gerald Scarzella, Timpview High; Thuy Uong, Point Loma High*

Bridging Design, Research, and Instruction: Iterative Curriculum Improvement in Statistics Education. *Claudia C. Sutter, CourseKata; Matthew Jackson; Adam B. Blake, University of California - Los Angeles; James W. Stigler, University of California - Los Angeles; Karen B. Givvin, University of California - Los Angeles*

Chair: *Claudia C. Sutter, CourseKata*

Discussant: *James W. Stigler, University of California - Los Angeles*

57.076-8. Data Use: For Whom and For What? (Table 8). SIG-Data-Driven Decision Making in Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Centering Teacher Expertise for Data Interpretation in Schools for the Deaf or Hard of Hearing. *Sudip Ghosh, Pennsylvania State University; Simon Hooper, Pennsylvania State University; Leo Jian Liao, Pennsylvania State University; Susan Rose, University of Minnesota; Rayne A. Sperling, Pennsylvania State University*

The Voice Paradox: How Student Perception Surveys Silence

the Voices They Claim to Capture. *Moriah Omer-Attali, The Hebrew University of Jerusalem*

Clustering California: Unpacking Arts Education Policy, Data Plausibility, and District Performance. *Lindsey Kunisaki, University of California - Los Angeles; Vinh Quang Tran, St. John's University; Gulnur Ozbek, St. John's University*

Chair: *Kavya Sree Mariboyina, Little Priest Tribal College*

57.076-9. Methodological Attunements: Listening, Mapping, and Reflexive Inquiry (Table 9). SIG-Qualitative Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Dadirri and Pauline Oliveros: The Significance of Deep Listening and (Educational) Qualitative Research. *Walter S. Gershon, Rowan University*

Collaborative concept mapping method for evolving and conflicting understandings in school safety leadership. *Jennifer Classen, Dalhousie University*

Tracing the Theoretical High: Cruel Optimism and the Promise of Relational Inquiry. *Jessica Van Cleave, Gardner-Webb University; Hilary E. Hughes, University of Georgia*

Chair: *Susan N. Nordstrom, University of Alabama*

Discussant: *Astri Napitupulu, University of Missouri - St. Louis*

57.076-10. Understanding Science Achievement Using Large-Scale and Longitudinal Data (Table 10). Division C - Learning and Instruction; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

An Accelerated Longitudinal Design Study Examining Emotional Engagement toward Learning Science from Grades 3 through 12. *Robert H. Tai, Australian Catholic University; Ji Hoon Ryoo, Yonsei University; Xin Xia, University of Georgia; John Almarode, James Madison University; Adam V. Maltese, Indiana University; Katherine P. Dabney, Virginia Commonwealth University*

Predicting Science Achievement: A Machine Learning Approach to PISA Data Analysis Across 2006 and 2015. *Zeynep Menteshoglu, University of Iowa; Hyesun You, University of Iowa*

Predictors of Korean Students' Science Achievement PISA 2022: A Post-Selection Inference Approach. *Nam-Hwa Kang, Korea National University of Education; Minjeong Rho, Korea National University of Education*

Urban/Rural Science Achievement Disparities: A Causal Forest Analysis of Low-Performing Students in TIMSS 2023. *Li Zhu, University of Iowa; Zhenhan Fang, University of Iowa; Mingyu Huang, University of Iowa*

57.077. AERA Poster Session Friday 1:45 pm; Poster Session

57.077-1. Curricula, Culture, and Critical Pedagogy: Insights from Chemistry to Social Justice. Division B - Curriculum Studies; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 1:45-3:15pm

Posters:

1. Academic Mentorship Matters: The Intellectual Exchange between Harris and Young Dewey (Poster 1). *Yi-Ping Lo, Chinese Culture University; Wen-jing Shan, Chinese Culture University*
2. Establishing an Academic Minor in Emergency Management (Poster 2). *Peter G. Kreysa, California State University - Long Beach*
3. How Textbooks Support Competency-Based Curriculum? A Comparative Study of Four Chemistry Textbooks in China (Poster 3). *Helen Gao, East China Normal University*
4. The Worst Sort of Lynching: Literacy as Resistance to Curriculum Violence (Poster 4). *Tilifayea Griffin, Georgia State University*
5. Time and Connection: The White Rose Movement as Transgenerational Activist Pedagogy (Poster 5). *Timothy Martin, Simon Fraser University; Jake Burdick, Purdue University*

57.077-2. Instructional Design, Feedback, and Learning Strategies. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 1:45-3:15pm

Posters:

6. Educating for Meta-Reasoning: An Instructional Intervention to Support Adaptive Cognition (Poster 6). *Gabe Avakian Orona, Boston College*
7. Essay Writing Process and Quality in Word vs. ChatGPT Argumentative Writing (Poster 7). *Jennifer G. Cromley, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Martin Lehrer, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Timothy Thieme, Parkland College; Matt Gadbury, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Pooja Roy, University of Houston*
8. Promoting Categorization of Statistics Word Problems Through Practice with Feedback and Examples (Poster 8). *Michael Osfeld, University of California - Santa Barbara; Richard E. Mayer, University of California - Santa Barbara*
9. Prompt Characteristics and Student Essay Scores in a ChatGPT Writing Task (Poster 9). *Jennifer G. Cromley, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Matt Gadbury, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Pooja Roy, University of Houston*
10. Sequencing Problem-Solving and Worked Examples: Effects on Performance, Cognitive Load and Judgments of

Division and SIG Posters

Learning (Poster 10). *Ines Zeithofer, Paris Lodron University Salzburg*

11. The Effects of Learner Choice and Concept Map Formats on Chemistry Outcomes (Poster 11). *Oluwafemi J. Sunday, Washington State University; Oluwafemi J Ajeigbe, Texas A&M University; Chloe G. Dydasco, Washington State University*
12. When Failure Prevails: Benefits of Exploration on Learning and Metacognition (Poster 12). *Ryan James Patrick, University of Georgia; Marci S. DeCaro, University of Louisville*
13. A Three-Level Meta-Analysis on the Effect of Learner-Generated Summarizing on Engagement and Learning Outcomes (Poster 13). *Lijia Lin, University of Macau*
14. Does Structure-Guided Highlighting Improve Learning from Expository Text? An Eye-Tracking Study with 7th Grade Students (Poster 14). *Hector R. Ponce, University of Santiago of Chile*
15. Do the Effects of Teachers' Performance-Approach Goals Vary by Their Underlying Reasons for Goal Pursuit? (Poster 15). *Sori Hwang, The Ohio State University; YoonJung Cho, Sungshin Women's University; Sungok Serena Shim, Ball State University; YoonJung Cho, Sungshin Women's University*
16. How Praise Type Moderates Motivation-Engagement Relationships: An Eye-Tracking Study (Poster 16). *Minghui Wang, University of California - Riverside; Pamela Sheffler, Landmark College; Matthew Kersting, University of California - Riverside; Kalina Michalska, University of California - Riverside; Cecilia Cheung, University of California - Riverside*
17. Visual Representations in College Classrooms: Faculty Perception of Student Representational Competencies and Pedagogy (Poster 17). *Zachary A. Myers, Pennsylvania State University; Aluwesi Ledua Volau Fonolahi, Pennsylvania State University; Melissa Hicks, Pennsylvania State University; Peggy N. Van Meter, Pennsylvania State University*
18. Writing with Generative AI: An Exploration of Strategies Use and Writing Performance in Source-based Writing (Poster 18). *SeongYeup Kim, Pennsylvania State University; Matthew T. McCrudden, Pennsylvania State University*
19. Explaining to the Bored Audience Promotes Learning-by-Teaching (Poster 19). *Xinyi Yin, Central China Normal University; Meixia Cheng, Central China Normal University; Xiaoxue Leng, Central China Normal University; Fuxing Wang, Central China Normal University*
20. Students' Overwhelming Resistance to Cumulative Quizzing (Poster 20). *Alexis Richmond, University of Texas at Austin; Veronica X. Yan, University of Texas at Austin*

57.077-3. Examining the use of generative AI in educational contexts. Division C - Learning and Instruction
Cosponsored with Division C - Learning and Instruction,

Division C - Learning and Instruction; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall -
Exhibit Hall A; 1:45-3:15pm

Posters:

21. Empowering the Future of STEM Education: A Systematic Review of AI Integration Facilitators and Barriers (Poster 21). *Atefeh Ataran, Clemson University; Ladan Shojaei, Indiana University*
22. Who Benefits Most from AI Education? Exploring the Interaction of Student Agency and Formal Learning (Poster 22). *Siya LIANG, Chinese University of Hong Kong; King Woon YAU, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Ching Sing Chai, Chinese University of Hong Kong*
23. Understanding GenAI Beliefs of International Teachers in the US, India, Qatar, Colombia, and the Philippines (Poster 23). *Rosie Le Xiu, University of Southern California; Stephen J. Aguilar, University of Southern California; Reem Al-Sulaiti, world innovation summit for education (WISE); Maimoona Junjuna, World Innovation Summit for Education (WISE); Selma Talha-Jebril, World Innovation Summit for Education (WISE)*
24. A Systematic Review on How to Design K-12 Artificial Intelligence Education (Poster 24). *Xin Liu, East China Normal University; Zhuotao Lu, Qingdao University; Shuai LIU, East China Normal University; Yihe Gao, East China Normal University; Xiaozhe Yang, East China Normal University*
25. "What Would You Ask an AI Expert?": A Simple Question Reveals Complex K-12 Student Thinking (Poster 25). *Shuchi Grover, Looking Glass Ventures*

57.077-4. Interactive and Integrative Practices to Improve Teaching and Learning in Elementary & Secondary Contexts. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Poster Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall -
Exhibit Hall A; 1:45-3:15pm

Posters:

26. Everyday Ways of Knowing in Middle Schoolers' Emergent Historical Practice of Evaluating Evidence for Argumentation (Poster 26). *Sida Sun, University of Michigan*
27. Becoming Seen, Becoming Self: A Symbolic Interactionist Analysis of African American High School Students' Identity Negotiation During Study Abroad in China (Poster 27). *Lijuan Shi, Bard High School Early College; Shenika Hankerson, University of Maryland; Kym Sturdivant, DC Public Schools; Yuming Deng, Bard High School Early College; Yuan Gao, Bard High School Early College*
28. Teaching the unthinkable: Using digital media to improve student understanding of nuclear weapons history (Poster 28). *Joshua Littenberg-Tobias, GBH; Kensy Jordan, GBH*
29. Taiwanese Classroom Teachers' Beliefs, Attitudes, and Practices Regarding Music Integration (Poster 29). *You-Ling*

Wang, Indiana University

30. Speculative Civics For The Future: “I imagine a future where everyone has a home” (Poster 30). *Sophia Cayuso, University of Miami; Matt DeRoo, Florida International University; Jennifer Beth Kahn, University of Miami*
31. Project-Based Learning in Civic Education: Creating a New “Environment” to Promote Students’ Civic Engagement (Poster 31). *Weiyang Gao, University of Hong Kong*

57.077-5. Research Exploring Contextual Influences across the Lifespan: Grounded in Theories of Human Development.

Division E - Counseling and Human Development; Poster Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 1:45-3:15pm

Posters:

32. Enhancing Psychological Needs Through Minecraft Metaverse: A Pilot With Neurodiverse Children Experiencing School Attendance Problems (Poster 32). *Nobuko Demura, Yokohama City University*
33. Examining the Joint Roles of Racial-Ethnic and Science Socialization on College Students’ STEM Academic Functioning (Poster 33). *Jingyi Yuan, University of Rochester; Nestor Tulagan, University of Rochester*
34. Exploring Factors Influencing Digital Media Addiction Among Korean Adolescents (Poster 34). *Eunkyung Lee, University of North Texas*
35. Linking Housing Quality Concerns and Toddler Inhibitory Control: The Mediating Role of Household Disorganization (Poster 35). *Nathaniel Philip Pettit, University of Pittsburgh; Jazelle Pilato, University of Pittsburgh; Elizabeth Votruba-Drzal, University of Pittsburgh; Melissa Libertus, University of Pittsburgh; Heather J. Bachman, University of Pittsburgh*
36. Out of Sight, Not Mind?: A Mixed Methods Investigation of Yondr Pouches and Student Well-Being (Poster 36). *Kathy Chau Rohn, University of New Hampshire; Adam M. McCready, University of Connecticut; Jennifer Phaiah, Sacred Heart University; Kelly Farrell, UConn; Alanna Torres-Laboy, University of Connecticut*
37. Parent-child Mental State Talk and Narrative Comprehension: Evidence from Naturalistic Conversations with Chinese Preschoolers (Poster 37). *Yifei Phoebe Wang, University of California - Los Angeles; Yawen Yu, University of California - Los Angeles; Alison L. Bailey, University of California - Los Angeles*
38. Parent-Student Perception Gaps and Behavioral Risk in Vocational Schools (Poster 38). *Margot Zanetti, Pegaso University; Stefania Morsanuto, Pegaso University; Francesco Peluso Cassese, Università Telematica Pegaso; Pierpaolo Limone, Università Telematica Pegaso*
39. Somatic Registration: An Embodied Framework for Learning to Cross Relational Thresholds (Poster 39). *Na'im Shahid Eggleston, Praxia Relational Research Lab*
40. Teachers' Retirement Phase: A Longitudinal Qualitative

Study (Poster 40). *Meirav Hauben, Tel Aviv University; Rachel Cinamon Gali, Tel-Aviv University*

41. The Role of Spatial Activity Engagement in Early Spatial Development: Examining Gender Differences during Preschool (Poster 41). *Joeli Angelina Camarote, University of Pittsburgh; Jazelle A Pilato, University of Pittsburgh; Melissa Libertus, University of Pittsburgh; Elizabeth Votruba-Drzal, University of Pittsburgh; Heather J. Bachman, University of Pittsburgh*
42. Understanding Medical Staff Experiences and Perspectives on Child Language Brokers Translating Medical Information (Poster 42). *Ines M. Torres, University of California - Los Angeles*
43. Attitudes and perceptions of childhood vaccinations among Latinx and Black prospective parents (Poster 43). *Becky Ontiveros, California State University - Northridge; Jade Cuevas, California State University - Northridge; David Wakefield, California State University - Northridge; April Z. Taylor, California State University - Northridge*
44. Children's Intergroup Preferences at the Intersection of Race/Ethnicity, Gender, Gender Expression, and Social Class (Poster 44). *Negin Ghavami, Loyola Marymount University; Dzorghenyui Adzo Gbagbo, Loyola Marymount University; Colson Lee, Loyola Marymount University; Ryan Anderson, Loyola Marymount University; Sandra Graham, University of California - Los Angeles*
45. Differential Trajectories of Social-Emotional Competence in Early Adolescence: The Role of Mindfulness (Poster 45). *Yonghe TI, University of Hong Kong; Cong Yi, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Shun-Lam Chan, Tsinghua University; Jun Wei, Tsinghua University*
46. Psycho-social Factors Influencing Children’s Attitudes toward People with Disabilities in Inclusive Classrooms (Poster 46). *Lily L. Dyson, University of Victoria*

57.077-6. Research Implications for Teaching and Teacher Ed Policy and Practice - Div K Sec 10.

Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Poster Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 1:45-3:15pm

Posters:

47. Understanding Preservice Teacher’s Decision to Choose Rural STEM Teaching: A Survey Validation (Poster 47). *Dana P. Franz, Mississippi State University; Diana Cumings Outlaw, Mississippi State University; Devon G. Brenner, Mississippi State University; Jennifer G. Whitfield, Texas A&M University*
48. When Trust Becomes Risk: Governing Affects in Teacher-Parent Interaction in China (Poster 48). *Xinyue Zhou, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Jia Ren, East China Normal University; Hui Dong, East China Normal University*

57.077-7. Mapping Teacher Labor Demand: Real-Time

Analysis of Job Postings in Wyoming. Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 1:45-3:15pm

Poster:

49. Mapping Teacher Labor Demand: Real-Time Analysis of Job Postings Across Wyoming School Districts (Poster 49).
Mark A. Perkins, University of Colorado - Colorado Springs; Bolaji Aderibigbe Akorede, University of Wyoming

57.077-8. Developing AI Literacy and Teacher Professional Competence. SIG-Technology as an Agent of Change in Teaching and Learning; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 1:45-3:15pm

Posters:

50. Embodied Arts-Integrated AI Literacy: A Nested Mixed-Methods Preliminary Study With K-12 Educators (Poster 50).
Stephen Emmanuel Abu, University of Alabama; Areezo Ghooreian, University of Alabama; Idowu David Awoyemi, University of Alabama; Jewoong Moon, University of Alabama
51. What Human Skills Will Be Essential in an AI-Facilitated Future of Teaching? Perspectives of Teachers (Poster 51).
Teresa M. Ober, Educational Testing Service; Michael Flor, Educational Testing Service; Patrick C. Kyllonen, Educational Testing Service; Matthew S. Johnson, Educational Testing Service; Kyoungwon Seo, Seoul National University of Science and Technology; Ido Roll, Technion & ETS
52. Ethical Competencies for K-12 teachers to integrate AI Literacy: Insights from a Systematic Literature Review (Poster 52).
Tirtha Karki, Purdue University; Deepti Tagare, University of Texas - San Antonio; Wonjin Yu, Purdue University
53. Teacher Professional Development on AI Integration: A Qualitative Study of Programs and Pedagogies (Poster 53).
Ai-Chu Elisha Ding, University of Georgia; Jennifer Kleiman, University of Georgia; Ying Zhang, University of Georgia; Lehong Shi, University of Georgia; Kexin Zhang, University of Georgia; Zixian Jiang, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Xiaoming Zhai, University of Georgia
54. Generative AI in Teacher Education: Ethical and Pedagogical Perspectives from Australia and the United States. (Poster 54).
Luke Parker, Australian Catholic University; Jessica Holloway, Australian Catholic University; Steven Lewis, Australian Catholic University; Sarah Langman, Australian Catholic University; Deborah DeBuhr, Australian Catholic University; Kylie Vanderkley, Australian Catholic University
55. Designing with memory: Multi-Agent LLM systems for adaptive lesson planning in AI literacy education (Poster 55).
Xiaoxue Du, MIT Media Lab

57.078. e-Lightning Ed-Talk Session 13 - Stage 1. AERA e-Lightning Ed-Talks; AERA Ed Talk
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Exhibit Hall A - Stage 1; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Understanding GenAI Beliefs of International Teachers in the US, India, Qatar, Colombia, and the Philippines (Stage 1, 1:50 PM).
Rosie Le Xiu, University of Southern California; Stephen J. Aguilar, University of Southern California; Reem Al-Sulaiti, world innovation summit for education (WISE); Maimoona Junjuna, World Innovation Summit for Education (WISE); Selma Talha-Jebril, World Innovation Summit for Education (WISE)

How Praise Type Moderates Motivation-Engagement

Relationships: An Eye-Tracking Study (Stage 1, 1:59 PM).

Minghui Wang, University of California - Riverside; Pamela Sheffler, Landmark College; Matthew Kersting, University of California - Riverside; Kalina Michalska, University of California - Riverside; Cecilia Cheung, University of California - Riverside

Do the Effects of Teachers' Performance-Approach Goals Vary by Their Underlying Reasons for Goal Pursuit? (Stage 1, 2:08 PM).
Sori Hwang, The Ohio State University; YoonJung Cho, Sungshin Women's University; Sungok Serena Shim, Ball State University; YoonJung Cho, Sungshin Women's University

Does Structure-Guided Highlighting Improve Learning from Expository Text? An Eye-Tracking Study with 7th Grade Students (Stage 1, 2:17 PM).
Hector R. Ponce, University of Santiago of Chile

Sequencing Problem-Solving and Worked Examples: Effects on Performance, Cognitive Load and Judgments of Learning (Stage 1, 2:26 PM).
Ines Zeithofer, Paris Lodron University Salzburg

Promoting Categorization of Statistics Word Problems Through Practice with Feedback and Examples (Stage 1, 2:35 PM).

Michael Osfeld, University of California - Santa Barbara; Richard E. Mayer, University of California - Santa Barbara

Essay Writing Process and Quality in Word vs. ChatGPT

Argumentative Writing (Stage 1, 2:44 PM).
Jennifer G. Cromley, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Martin Lehrer, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Timothy Thieme, Parkland College; Matt Gadbury, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Pooja Roy, University of Houston

Educating for Meta-Reasoning: An Instructional Intervention to Support Adaptive Cognition (Stage 1, 2:53 PM).
Gabe Avakian Orona, Boston College

Chair: *Rand Quinn, University of Pennsylvania*

57.079. e-Lightning Ed-Talk Session 13 - Stage 2. AERA e-Lightning Ed-Talks; AERA Ed Talk
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Exhibit Hall A

- Stage 2; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

The Worst Sort of Lynching: Literacy as Resistance to Curriculum Violence (Stage 2, 1:50 PM). *Tilifayea Griffin, Georgia State University*

Establishing an Academic Minor in Emergency Management (Stage 2, 1:59 PM). *Peter G. Kreysa, California State University - Long Beach*

Taiwanese Classroom Teachers' Beliefs, Attitudes, and Practices Regarding Music Integration (Stage 2, 2:08 PM). *You-Ling Wang, Indiana University*

Teaching the unthinkable: Using digital media to improve student understanding of nuclear weapons history (Stage 2, 2:17 PM). *Joshua Littenberg-Tobias, GBH; Kensy Jordan, GBH*

The Role of Spatial Activity Engagement in Early Spatial Development: Examining Gender Differences during Preschool (Stage 2, 2:26 PM). *Joel Angelina Camarote, University of Pittsburgh; Jazelle A Pilato, University of Pittsburgh; Melissa Libertus, University of Pittsburgh; Elizabeth Votruba-Drzal, University of Pittsburgh; Heather J. Bachman, University of Pittsburgh*

Out of Sight, Not Mind?: A Mixed Methods Investigation of Yondr Pouches and Student Well-Being (Stage 2, 2:35 PM). *Kathy Chau Rohn, University of New Hampshire; Adam M. McCready, University of Connecticut; Jennifer Phaiath, Sacred Heart University; Kelly Farrell, UConn; Alanna Torres-Laboy, University of Connecticut*

What Human Skills Will Be Essential in an AI-Facilitated Future of Teaching? Perspectives of Teachers (Stage 2, 2:44 PM). *Teresa M. Ober, Educational Testing Service; Michael Flor, Educational Testing Service; Patrick C. Kyllonen, Educational Testing Service; Matthew S. Johnson, Educational Testing Service; Kyoungwon Seo, Seoul National University of Science and Technology; Ido Roll, Technion & ETS*

Ethical Competencies for K-12 teachers to integrate AI Literacy: Insights from a Systematic Literature Review (Stage 2, 2:53 PM). *Deepti Tagare, University of Texas - San Antonio; Tirtha Karki, Purdue University; Wonjin Yu, Purdue University*

Generative AI in Teacher Education: Ethical and Pedagogical Perspectives from Australia and the United States. (Stage 2, 3:02 PM). *Luke Parker, Australian Catholic University; Jessica Holloway, Australian Catholic University; Steven Lewis, Australian Catholic University; Sarah Langman, Australian Catholic University; Deborah DeBuhr, Australian Catholic University; Kylie Vanderkley, Australian Catholic University*

Chair: *Edmund T. Hamann, University of Nebraska - Lincoln*

57.080. AERA Research in Progress Roundtable Session

Three. AERA Sessions; Roundtable Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C; 1:45-3:15pm

57.080. Research-in-Progress RT001 (Friday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Adapting a Self-Report Bullying Victimization Measure for Individuals with Intellectual and Developmental Disability. *Austin Cameron Jackson, University of Missouri; Chad A. Rose, University of Missouri; Erica S. Lembke, University of Missouri*

Mind the Effort Gap: Identifying Measurement Bias with Item Differential Functioning. *Yuxi Shen, Georgetown University; Qiwei He, Georgetown University*

Predicting Differential Item Functioning with Machine Learning: Modeling Fairness Through Item and Context Features in PISA 2022. *Archangel Metadio Gundula, University of Nebraska - Lincoln; Jordan M. Wheeler, University of Nebraska - Lincoln*

Chair: *Laurence Parker, University of Utah*

57.080. Research-in-Progress RT012 (Friday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

A Social Relational approach to Specific Learning Disability: Identifying barriers for students with SLD. *Timothy Flewelling, Claremont Graduate University*

Empowering Educators: An International Exploration of Differentiated Instruction for d/Deaf and Hard of Hearing Students with Disabilities. *Katherine Wyble, Sunbelt Staffing*

Mexican and Mexican American Mothers and Fathers Experiences of Social Emotional Support for Young Children with Disabilities. *Stephanie Fernandez, University of Illinois at Chicago*

“Telling Stories” Of Disability Identity: Narrative Inquiry While Presuming Competence Of Adults With N/IDD. *Paige Richmond, University of Minnesota*

Chair: *David J. Francis, University of Houston*

57.080. Research-in-Progress RT018 (Friday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Are Branch Campuses a Dead End? Examining Degree Completion at Rural Branch Campuses and Centers. *Lindsey Clarice Ragsdale, University of Florida; Zyrashae N. Smith-Onyewu, University of Florida*

Uncategorized Sessions

Northern & Rural Ontario Academic Achievement Gaps. *Mostafa Awad, Toronto District School Board*
Rural Resistance: How Cultural Wealth Sustains Students' Persistence in Postsecondary Pathways. *Giovanna Lorenzi Pinto, Texas State University*

Chair: *Sheneka M. Williams, Michigan State University*

57.080. Research-in-Progress RT022 (Friday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

An Examination of Deficit Thinking in the Academy. *Breina Mosely, Harvard University*
Associations Between Ethnic-Racial Identity Attitudes and Mental Health Outcomes Among Adolescents with Chinese Heritage. *Shanyilin Jin, Harvard University; Hua Luo, Florida State University; Shiyi Ji, Florida State University*
Bridging Gaps in Ethnic-Racial Socialization: Developing a Psychoeducational Intervention for Transracial Adoptive Families. *Emma Keller, Stanford University*
Ethnic-Racial Socialization Practices Among Black Parents of Black-White Biracial Adolescents. *Dominique Leigh Callahan, University of California - Los Angeles*
Visualizing the 'Hood: Archiving and Imagining Futures Through Creative and Visual Arts in Black and Latine Communities. *Abigail Lopez-Byrd, University of California - Riverside*

Chair: *Latrise P. Johnson, University of Alabama*

57.080. Research-in-Progress RT028 (Friday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Disrupting What's Seen (and Unseen): Seeing Through Systems of Oppression. *Jade Johnson, University of Maryland; Mary Ziegler Zimmerman, University of Maryland; Blake O'Neal Turner, Marquette University; Margaret Walton, University of Maryland*
Exploring Pre-Service Mathematics Teachers' Perceptions of their Field Experiences: A Narrative Inquiry Design. *Steevenson Rosema, Old Dominion University*
Mindset-oriented Wise Interventions for Elementary Mathematics Preservice Teachers to Support Positive Beliefs about Challenges. *Sarvani Pemmaraju, Middle Tennessee State University*

57.080. Research-in-Progress RT034 (Friday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

How Black Males with Gang Affiliations Experience Trust in

Out-of-School Learning Environments. *Kevin M. Barry, Northwestern University*

Latine Migrant Children Navigating Post-Graduation Pathways. *Julybeth Murillo, University of California - Irvine*

Teaching Under Compounding Constraint: School-Level Influences on Teaching Pressures. *Suzanne E. Wood, University of Notre Dame*

Chair: *Elizabeth I. Rivera, Montclair State University*

57.080. Research-in-Progress RT041 (Friday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Assessment in Higher Education. *Abir Bousaid, Graduate Center - CUNY*
Navigating Anomie and Adaptation: A Practitioner's Sociological view on Career Transitions in University and Military Settings. *Ryan Sermon, U.S. Department of Labor*
The Washback Effect of the HSK Level 7-9: International Students' Perspectives in China. *Yiru Gong, University of Pennsylvania*

Chair: *Michal Kurlaender, University of California - Davis*

57.080. Research-in-Progress RT043 (Friday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Early-Career Faculty Members' Perception of Academic Freedom in Teaching. *Madeline M Rowe, University of Minnesota - Twin Cities*
Exploring Classroom Communication Stress and Coping among International Graduate-Student Course Instructors. *Kexin Jiang, Washington State University; Chad M. Gotch, Washington State University*
Exploring Higher Education Faculty Perceptions of and Experiences with Gamification in Online Learning. *Empress Searight, University of Alabama; Margaret L. Rice, University of Alabama*

Chair: *LaWanda W. Ward, Pennsylvania State University*

57.080. Research-in-Progress RT048 (Friday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

From Clinic to Classroom: Investigating the Alignment of IEPs with Diagnostic Clinical Evaluation Reports for Students with a Fetal Alcohol Spectrum Disorder Diagnosis. *Emalise Luzzo Mitchell, University of Washington*
SPED and ELL Backgrounds Among Enlisted Marines: Implications for PME Completion. *Lindsay M Reid, Stafford County Public Schools*

Understanding Contemplative Practice in Special Educator Well-Being. *Richard Williams, University at Buffalo - SUNY*
Chair: *Janet L. Miller, Teachers College, Columbia University*

57.080. Research-in-Progress RT051 (Friday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

"Feeling Professional:" Teacher Preparation Programs in the Face of Ethnic Studies Reforms. *Amy Gong Liu, University of California - Irvine*

Youth Organizing & Critical Hope in San Bernardino. *Ellen Parks, Vanderbilt University; Megan McCormick, Vanderbilt University*

Reclaiming the Classroom: Oaxacan Indigenous Students and the Limits of Ethnic Studies Implementation. *Jissel Antonio, San Jose State University*

Reframing Civic Education In A Post-COVID World: A Systematic Review of Scholarship (2020–2025). *Isaac B. Bolaji, Kent State University; Toyosi Stephen Adedara, Baylor University; Oluwabunmi Blessing Alao, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Busola Omolade-Adedara, University of Ibadan*

Chair: *Ruth Maria López, University of Arizona*

57.080. Research-in-Progress RT054 (Friday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Investing in Success? Family Educational Investment and PISA 2022 Math Achievement in Saudi Arabia. *Mohammed Alsuwaylih, University of Pittsburgh*

To Dream Together: Collective Future-Building in a West Bank Youth Program. *Catherine E. Pitcher, Harvard University*

Transnational Family Imaginaries: Chinese Families and Study Abroad. *Haizhao Bo, University of Chicago*

Chair: *Peter A. Youngs, University of Virginia*

57.080. Research-in-Progress RT060 (Friday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Co-Creating a Conceptual Model for Decolonizing Short-Term Education Abroad. *Kaitlyn Sky Wernik, Montana State University; Grace Epperson, Montana State University*

Coloniality and Carcerality in the Schooling Experiences of Formerly Incarcerated Adults in Puerto Rico. *Jazdil Poupart-Feliciano, Stanford University*

The Stories Ain't Storyin': Amplifying Black Students' Existential Narratives to Reimagine Postsecondary Transitional/Developmental Literacy Pedagogies. *Ellenar*

Harper, Texas Tech University

Chair: *Stephen D. Hancock, North Carolina A&T State University*

57.080. Research-in-Progress RT063 (Friday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

From CQ to Practice: A Quantitative Ethnography of Team Discourse. *Jonathan Freking, Pepperdine University*

From Repetition to Reflection: Research on Metacognitive Listening Strategies in Chinese High School Audiovisual Lessons. *Wanyue Shen, Shanghai Jiao Tong University; Xiaoqiao Zhang, Shanghai Jiao Tong University*

Investigating the Impact on Secondary Science Student Success of Using the Metacognition Technique of Monitoring. *Tracy Rendleman, University of Findlay*

Strategic Motivation and Learning Trajectories: How Promotion and Prevention Foci Shape Students' Metacognitive Monitoring Across a Semester. *Yucheng Bao, Vanderbilt University; Cristina D. Zepeda, Vanderbilt University*

Chair: *Jennifer Higgs, University of California - Davis*

57.080. Research-in-Progress RT068 (Friday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Cost-benefit analysis of re/classification of ELLs (English language learners): a case of high-school students. *Jeevan Karki, Michigan State University*

Examining Teachers' Awareness, Difficulties, and Collaboration in Fostering Family Involvement for English Learners (ELs). *Leah Bombin Matoka, University of Colorado - Colorado Springs*

From "I Am Novice" to "We Are Multilingual Teachers": Collaborative Autoethnography of Translanguaging Stance Development. *Yuzhou Xiong, University of Pennsylvania*
The Role of Language Ideologies in Saudi Elementary English Education: EFL teachers' perspectives and experiences. *Ghanem Alghuwainem, University of South Carolina*

Tracing Knowledge through 'Student-Generated Funds' and 'Positionings' in Adult ESL Contexts. *Thilina Indrajie Wickramaarachchi, University of Wyoming*

Chair: *Christian J. Faltis, Texas A&M International University*

57.080. Research-in-Progress RT072 (Friday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

From Absent to "Invisible" - Critical Discourse Analysis of New York State's Newly Revised "Attendance Index"

Policy. *Zheng Ma, New York University*

The Reading-Disabled Child: Constructed at the Intersection of Race, Class, and Reading Pedagogy; 1975 - 2004. *Deborah Lynam, Rutgers University - Camden*

Chair: *Genevieve P. Siegel-Hawley, Virginia Commonwealth University*

57.080. Research-in-Progress RT076 (Friday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

From Individualism and Competition to Cooperation and Solidarity: Can School Change This Paradigm? *Virginia Gomes, University of Maryland*

Simulating Children's Emergent Roles in Collaborative Learning through Multi-Agent Systems. *Xi Chen, Shanghai Jiao Tong University*

The Role of Psychological Capital in Collaborative Learning. *Yiting Chen, University of Pennsylvania; Qinmei Xu, Zhejiang University*

Chair: *David T. Hansen, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Friday, April 10th, 3:45 pm

Governance Meetings and Events

58.001. AERA Graduate Student Council: Closed Meeting.

AERA Governance; Governance Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 518;
3:45-5:15pm

Chair: *Cammie Justus-Smith, Virginia Commonwealth University*

58.002. AERA SIG Executive Committee: Closed Meeting.

AERA Governance; Governance Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 513;
3:45-5:15pm

Chair: *Norma A. Guzman, Texas A&M University - Kingsville*

Presidential Sessions

58.010. Futuring Scholarly Expression Through Sound, Sound Design, and Music: A Listening Session with Liner Notes. AERA Presidential Session; Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 403B;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

lovenloops: Time, Sound, Music and Black Girlhood. *Blair Ebony Smith, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Curriculum of the Mind: Research as Performance and Community-Based Artistry. *Stevie D. Johnson, The Ohio State University*

Time Stretching Memory: Haunting, Unforgetting, and Sound Design in the Audio Essay. *Brian Mooney, Fairleigh Dickinson University*

Crate Missions and the Hip Hop Producer's Ear: Listening, Legacy, and Beat-Making as Archival Practice. *Jason D. Rawls, The Ohio State University*

Sound Smear Across the Page: Opacity and Black Aesthetic Creation. *Ruth Nicole Brown, Michigan State University; Emery Marc Petchauer, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Chairs: *Emery Marc Petchauer, Teachers College, Columbia University; Ruth Nicole Brown, Michigan State University*

Discussants: *Lalitha Vasudevan, Teachers College, Columbia University; Haeny S. Yoon, Teachers College, Columbia University*

58.011. Stolen School: What Desegregation Took and One Black Community's Fight to Get it Back. AERA Presidential Session; Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 411 (Theatre); 3:45-5:15pm

Chair: *kihana miraya ross, Northwestern University*

Participants: *Shannon Paige Clark, University of Maryland - Eastern Shore; Laurice Bell, Shorefront Legacy Center; Oliver Ruff, Evanston / Skokie School District 65; Monique Parsons, McGaw YMCA*

58.012. Unforgetting the History of Racism and Education in the US: Imagining a Future for DEI and Multicultural Education Research, Policies, and Practices. AERA Presidential Session; Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 408A;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Surviving a Second Nadir: Resisting the Rightist Destruction of Democracy. *Gloria J. Ladson-Billings, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

DEI, Democracy, and the Authoritarian Threat: Why Higher Education Must Resist. *Royel M. Johnson, University of Southern California*

Rise of Fascism in the United States: A Critical Multicultural Anti-Fascist Response. *Michael Vavrus, Evergreen State College*

Possibilities and Obligations of Critical Scholars when Knowledge Production is Under Siege. *Michelle Fine, Graduate Center - CUNY*

Curriculum for a Diverse Democracy. *Christine E. Sleeter, California State University - Monterey Bay*

Redefining Membership: Executive Actions and the Boundaries

of Citizenship. *Angela M. Banks, William & Mary Law School*

DEI Disaster Recovery in America's K-12 Schools and Higher Education Institutions. *Shaun R. Harper, University of Southern California*

Chair: *James A. Banks, University of Washington*

Discussant: *Tyrone C. Howard, University of California - Los Angeles*

AERA Research and Science Policy Sessions

58.013. Reimagining the Institute of Education Sciences: Reflections and Perspectives from the Field. AERA Science and Policy Sessions; Invited Speaker Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 406AB;
3:45-5:15pm

Chair: *Michal Kurlaender, University of California - Davis*

Participants: *Adam Gamoran, William T. Grant Foundation; Nicole Patton-Terry, Florida State University; Kristabel Stark, University of Vermont; Michelle Crosby, American Statistical Association*

AERA Sessions

58.014. 2025 Distinguished Contributions to Research in Education Award Lecture: Actionable and relevant education science: Focus on people, processes, and contexts that foster students' learning and development. AERA Sessions; Invited Speaker Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 408B;
3:45-5:15pm

Chair: *Deborah Loewenberg Ball, University of Michigan*

Presenter: *Robert Pianta, University of Virginia*

58.015. Remembering Jim Popham: His Scholarship, Leadership, and Commitment to Students. AERA Sessions; Invited Speaker Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 501B;
3:45-5:15pm

Chair: *Eva L. Baker, University of California - Los Angeles*

Participants: *Joan L. Herman, University of California - Los Angeles; James W. Pellegrino, University of Illinois at Chicago; Christina A. Christie, University of California - Los Angeles; Scott F. Marion, Center for Assessment*

Division Sessions

58.016. Leadership for Organizational Change and School Improvement. Division A - Administration; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Los Cerritos; 3:45-

5:15pm

Participants:

School Renewal in Outperforming and Underperforming Schools: A Comparative Analysis. *Jianping Shen, Western Michigan University; Siche Feng, Western Michigan University; Patricia L. Reeves, Western Michigan University; Xin Ma, University of Kentucky*

Reimagining Educational Leadership: Leadership as a Lever for Human Rights in Ontario's Public Education System.

Shezadi Khushal, University of Toronto - OISE

Complexity Leadership Practices for Inclusive Chinese

Immersion Preschool Professional Learning Communities.
Chu Hsi Tseng, San Francisco State University

Balancing Accountability and Creativity Through Shared Instructional Leadership and Principal Value on Creativity.

Xi Zhan, Nanjing University; Joonkil Ahn, University of Arizona; Xiaomeng Liu, Xiamen University

Chair: *Koksai Banoglu, The Education University of Hong Kong*

Discussant: *James C. Bridgeforth, University of Delaware*

58.017. Preparing Equity-Oriented Leaders Through the Education Doctorate (EdD). Division A - Administration; Paper Session

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, San Fernando; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Policy, Power, and Praxis: Co-Designing Leadership

Curriculum for Equity in a CPED-Aligned EdD Program.

Katherine C. Rodela, Washington State University; Shannon M. Calderone, Washington State University

Preparing Equity-Oriented Leaders: Critical Race Theory & Applied Research in the EdD. *Reginald D. Wilkerson, College of William & Mary; Jill Alexa Perry, Carnegie Project on the Education Doctorate*

The Theory-Practice Gap: Ed.D. Student-Practitioners' Perceptions of Culturally Responsive Leadership for Black and Latinx Students. *Inez Moore, California State University - Fullerton; Keyla Sanchez, California State University - Fullerton; Araceli Negrete, California State University - Fullerton; Wendy Heredia, California State University - Fullerton*

Tracing Ten Years of Dissertations in an Urban EdD Program:

Trends, Tensions, and Transformations. *Jody N. Polleck, Hunter College - CUNY; Jenny Tuten, Hunter College - CUNY; Nery Miluska Manrique Alcantara, Hunter College*

Discussant: *Lauren P. Bailes, University of Delaware*

58.018. Systems Change for Equity: Insights from Design, Network, and Continuous Improvement Approaches.

Division A - Administration; Paper Session

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Los Feliz; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Capitalizing on the Learning Potential of Intentional Networks to Advance Leadership for Equity. *Brooke Fousek,*

University of Texas at Austin; Yu-Yuan Huang, National Taipei University of Education; Daniella Molle, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Yi-Hwa Liou, National Taipei University of Education; Aziz Awaludin, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Christopher Saldaña, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Joshua Childs, University of Texas at Austin

Co-Designing for Equity: Examining Relationships and Dynamics in Design-Based Activities Embedded in Equity-Centered RPPs. *Tia R. Williams, Vanderbilt University; Richard O. Welsh, Vanderbilt University; Ashlynn Nash, Vanderbilt University*

District-School Relationships in Continuous Improvement: Evidence from Michigan. *Su Yon Choi, Michigan State University*

Pursuing Equitable Education and Learning Systems: The Promise of Continuous Improvement and Design Methods. *Maxwell Yurkofsky, Radford University; Meredith I. Honig, University of Washington; Noy Sabag, University of Washington; Jal David Mehta, Harvard University*

Chair: *Anysia P. Mayer, California State University, Stanislaus*

Discussant: *Jose Eos Trinidad, University of California - Berkeley*

58.019. The Roots and Development of Leadership: Special Interest Group Founders and Former Chairs. Division A - Administration; Invited Speaker Session
Westin Bonaventure, Level 2, Mt. Washington; 3:45-5:15pm

Chairs: *Leslie Ann Locke, Minnesota State University - Mankato; Detra DeVerne Johnson, University of Houston; Nakia M. Gray-Nicolas, Queens College - CUNY*

Participants: *Mariela Aime Rodriguez, University of Texas - San Antonio; Susan C. Faircloth, Two Feathers Consulting, LLC.; Sonya D. Hayes, University of Tennessee; Bryan A. VanGronigen, University of Delaware; Liliana E. Castrellon, San José State University; Angel Miles Nash, Wallace Foundation; Shelby A. Cosner, University of Georgia; Jim Scheurich, Indiana University - Indianapolis; Sonya Horsford, H&H Strategies; Jennie Weiner, University of Connecticut; Kristin Shawn Huggins, Washington State University; Erin Anderson, University of Denver; Rosa L. Rivera-McCutchen, Hunter College - CUNY*

58.020. Love and Power: A Curriculum of Black Joy. Division B - Curriculum Studies; Invited Speaker Session
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Beaudry B; 3:45-5:15pm

Chair: *Theodora Regina Berry, Bloomfield College of Montclair State University*

Discussants: *Theodora Regina Berry, Bloomfield College of Montclair State University; Boni Wozolek, Pennsylvania State University - Abington*

Panelists: *Justin A. Coles, University of Massachusetts - Amherst; Nichole A. Guillory, Kennesaw State University; Asilia K. Franklin-Phipps, SUNY - College at New Paltz; David O. Stovall, University of Illinois at Chicago*

58.021. Ancestral Prolepsis: Cultivating Relational Learning with Land and Generations for Indigenous and Planetary Futures. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Symposium
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Beaudry A; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Ancestral Seeding: Indigenous Stories as Dispersals for Sovereignty, Self-determination and Relational Wellbeing. *Cecelia Hoffman, Northwestern College; Megan Bang, Northwestern University*

River as Relative: The Mutually Constitutive Roles of Physical and Psychological Closeness in Water Education. *Forrest Bruce, Northwestern University*

Educational Assessment as Relational Learning Towards Ancestral Flourishing. *Miguel Angel Garcia-Bocanegra, Northwestern University; Anna Lees, University of Washington*

Chair: *Megan Bang, Northwestern University*

Discussant: *Anna Lees, University of Washington*

58.022. Building New Worlds: Constructing Supportive Spaces for Historically Marginalized Students and Faculty of Color. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, La Cienega; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Im Talkin' Bout ... Innit: Black Girls Creating and Building New World in the Third Space. *Briana Green, Michigan State University; Joanna N. Ali, North Carolina State University; Brittani Clark, North Carolina State University*

Asset-Based Frameworks to Examine the Belonging Experiences of Black and Latine Students: A Narrative Review. *Brooke Harris-Thomas, University of Michigan - Dearborn; Korinthia D. Nicolai, Indiana University; Xiao-Yin Chen, University of Tennessee; Christina Areizaga Barbieri, University of Delaware*

Centering Relationships for Student Support in an Underserved School Context. *Daneille Stacy-Ann Green, University College London - IOE*

Behind the Mask and Beneath the Armor: Engineering Faculty of Color Defining and Coping with Whiteness. *R. Jamaal Downey, University of San Diego; Joel Alejandro Mejia, University of Cincinnati; Diana Chen, University of San Diego; Gordon Hoople, University of San Diego*

Chair: *Martinique Ann Sealy Mitchell, Virginia Commonwealth University*

Discussant: *Taylor Cummings, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*

58.023. Debating the Future: Appropriate Use of Generative AI in Educational Research. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Symposium

Westin Bonaventure, Level 2, Beverly; 3:45-5:15pm

Chairs: *Matthew L. Bernacki, University of North Carolina -*

Chapel Hill; Alyssa Emery, Iowa State University; Helenrose Fives, Montclair State University; Jeff A. Greene, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill

Participants: Ha Nguyen, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Candace A. Walkington, Southern Methodist University; Stephen J. Aguilar, University of Southern California

58.024. Innovating K–12 Teaching and Learning with Generative AI: Insights From IES-funded National R&D Centers.

Division C - Learning and Instruction; Structured Poster Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 515A; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

1. AIRE: AI Reading Enhancer for Personalized Decodable Texts in Early Literacy (Poster 1). Zhaohui Li, Pennsylvania State University; Qingxiao Zheng, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Dancheng Liu, Buffalo State - SUNY; Tanya M. Christ, East Carolina University; John Z. Strong, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Laura S. Tortorelli, Michigan State University; X. Christine Wang, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Abeer Alwan, University of California - Los Angeles; Dilek Hakkani Tur, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Jinjun Xiong, University at Buffalo - SUNY
2. Imagining Futures for Early Literacy and Responsible AI: Results from CELaRAI's Year 1 Exploratory Study (Poster 2). Tanya M. Christ, East Carolina University; Laura S. Tortorelli, Michigan State University; John Z. Strong, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Lisa Cortez Hendricks, Michigan State University; Danielle Alexander, Oakland University; Maureen Bender, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Anthonia Ojeh, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Jessica Chan, University of Oxford; Amber Lawson, Bowling Green State University; Xintian Tu-Shea, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Jaekyung Lee, University at Buffalo - SUNY; X. Christine Wang, University at Buffalo - SUNY
3. Responsible AI in K–12 Education: A Policy Review (Poster 3). Zhuoyun Cai, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Zeyu Tang, Stanford University; X. Christine Wang, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Sanmi Koyejo, Stanford University; Ari Hock, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Angelina Wang, Stanford University; Kristen Smigielski, University at Buffalo - SUNY / CELaRAI; Christopher Hoadley, University at Buffalo - SUNY
4. A Framework for Generative AI-based Cognitive Engagement (Poster 4). Lehong Shi, University of Georgia; Shuchen Guo, Nanjing Normal University; Yizhu Gao, University of Georgia; Hongmei Li, Yunnan Normal University; Liang Zhang, University of Georgia; Ninghao Liu, University of Georgia; Xiaoming Zhai, University of Georgia
5. Demo: Integrating GenAI-Driven Feedback to Support the Science Practice of Developing and Using Models (Poster

5). Field Watts, Educational Testing Service; Ehsan Latif, University of Georgia; Zhaoji Wang, University of Georgia; Lei Liu, Educational Testing Service; Xiaoming Zhai, University of Georgia

6. Interactive Machine Learning and Conversational Agents for Supporting Scientific Inquiry in Secondary Education (Poster 6). Matias Ignacio Rojas, University of Georgia; Xiaoming Zhai, University of Georgia
7. Colleague.AI: An Educational Platform with AI Assistants as Knowledgeable Colleagues for Educators and Friendly Buddies for Learners (Poster 7). Alex Liu, University of Washington; Lief Esbenschade, University of Washington; Shawon Sarkar, University of Washington; Zewei Tian, University of Washington; Zachary Zhang, Colleague.ai; Kevin He, Colleague.ai; Min Sun, University of Washington
8. Understanding Teachers' Use of Generative AI in Math and Science Instruction (Poster 8). Shawon Sarkar, University of Washington; Lief Esbenschade, University of Washington; Drew Nucci, WestEd; Sarah Nielsen, WestEd; Ann R. Edwards, WestEd; Joshua Rosenberg, University of Tennessee; Alex Liu, University of Washington; Zewei Tian, University of Washington; Zachary Zhang, Colleague.ai; Kevin He, Colleague.ai; Min Sun, University of Washington
9. AmplifyGAIN: National Capacity-Building for Trustworthy AI in Education (Poster 9). Shawon Sarkar, University of Washington; Lief Esbenschade, University of Washington; Min Sun, University of Washington; Alex Liu, University of Washington; Zewei Tian, University of Washington; Kevin He, Colleague.ai; Zachary Zhang, Colleague.ai
10. U-GAIN Reading Overview and Demonstration (Poster 10). Jeremy Roschelle, Digital Promise Global; Adam Porsch, Amira
11. Educators' Use of AI Tools for Literacy: Uncovering Opportunities and Challenges for English Learners (Poster 11). Danae Kamdar, Digital Promise; Tiffany Leones, Digital Promise; Stefani Pautz Stephenson, Digital Promise; Ximena Dominguez, Digital Promise
12. Organizing Practitioner-Centered National Leadership to Support the Use of AI-Enabled Technology to Implement the Science of Reading (Poster 12). Yenda Prado, Digital Promise; Pati Ruiz, Digital Promise; Joshua Ddamulira, Digital Promise

Chair: X. Christine Wang, University at Buffalo - SUNY

Discussant: Victor R. Lee, Stanford University

58.025. Understanding and Supporting Feedback Uptake: Bridging Research and Practice in Educational Contexts.

Division C - Learning and Instruction; Symposium Westin Bonaventure, Level 3, Avalon; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Epistemic Emotions and Moves: Processing Peer Feedback in Science Learning. Jinzhi Zhou, Indiana University; Cindy E. Hmelo-Silver, Indiana University; Joshua Adam Danish, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Aman Desai,

University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign; Qiuyu Lin, Rutgers University; Ravit Golan Duncan, Rutgers University; Clark A. Chinn, Rutgers University

Dialogue Matters: The Effects of Feedback Dialogue and Dialogue Modality on Peer Feedback Quality and Uptake. *Christian D. Schunn, University of Pittsburgh; Yuhuan Emma Zhao, Northeast Normal University; Fuhui Zhang, Northeast Normal University*

How Students Perceive and Respond to GenAI for Peer Feedback Uptake. *Omid Noroozi, Wageningen University and Research; Golnoush Haddadian, Georgia State University; Xingshi Gao, Wageningen University; Christian D. Schunn, University of Pittsburgh; Maryam Alqassab, Open Universiteit Netherlands; Seyyed Kazem Banihashem, Open Universiteit Nederland*

Investigating Students' Knowledge of Revision Strategies and Encouraging Use in an Online Inquiry Science Unit. *Sarah Bichler, Ludwig Maximilian University Munich; Katharina Marie Bach, University of Munich; Marcia Linn, University of California - Berkeley; Allison Bradford, University of California - Berkeley*

Chair: *Sarah Bichler, Ludwig Maximilian University Munich*
Discussant: *Ingo Kollar, University of Augsburg*

58.026. Imagining Futures: AI, Technology, and the Changing Landscape of School Counseling. Division E - Counseling and Human Development; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 301A;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

AI Readiness Among School Counselors-in-Training: Knowledge, Self-Efficacy, and Ethical Preparedness Within the ASCA National Model Framework. *Cameka Hazel, New York Institute of Technology - CUNY; Sherri Barrow, Ball State University; Al Robiullah, Ball State University*

A Decade of Change: Tracking School Counselor Technology Use from 2013 to 2025. *Tracy M. Steele, Stanford Online High School*

Strengthening School Counseling Intervention Implementation: A Thematic Analysis of ChatGPT's Recommendations.

Jeffrey M. Warren, North Carolina Central University

School Counselors and AI: An Exploration of AI Tool Use in School Counseling. *Rachel L. Geesa, Ball State University; Carol A. Dahir, New York Institute of Technology; Serena J. Salloum, Ball State University*

Chair: *Rachel L. Geesa, Ball State University*

Discussant: *Angie Hickman, American School Counselor Association*

58.027. Mental Health and Resilience across Developmental Contexts. Division E - Counseling and Human Development; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304A;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Bias-Based Bullying and Adolescent Well-Being: A Person-Centered Analysis of Co-occurring Trajectories. *Gabriel Joey Merrin, Syracuse University; Ashleigh Jones, Syracuse University; Bo Jian, University of Pennsylvania; Chenhao Zhang, Syracuse University; SSophia Nowlan, Syracuse University; Melissa K. Holt, Boston University*

Measurement and Prediction of Stress-Related Growth in a Post-Pandemic College Sample. *Thomas J. Bischoff, Temple University; Xu Jiang, Temple University*

Seeking Help: Exploring Mental Health Experiences and Healthcare Service Awareness. *Emmanuel Chisom Okolo, Texas A&M University; Amber Kearney, Texas A&M University; Gary Wingenbach, Texas A&M University; Josephine Engels, Mental Health America of Greater Houston; Andrea Usanga, Mental Health America of Greater Houston*

“We Understand, But Need Support”: Teachers' Perspectives on Trauma-Informed Practices in Universal Transitional Kindergarten. *Ella Rho, University of Maryland; Krandhasi Kodaiarasu, University of Maryland; Chunyan Yang, University of Maryland; Xueqin Lin, University of California - Berkeley; Quennie Dong, University of California - Berkeley; Rebecca Cheung, University of California - Berkeley*

Chair: *Rika Marita Leilani Meyer, California State University - Northridge*

Discussant: *Zena R. Mello, San Francisco State University*

58.028. Solidarity is a Verb: Karen Lewis and the Long Fight for Public Education. Division F - Historical Inquiry in Education; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 511AB;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

The Impact of the Black Power Movement on Black Educators and Black Education. *Carol D. Lee, Northwestern University*
Black Women's Leadership in Urban Education. *Camika Royal, Morgan State University*

“The Foundation of Union Work is Classroom Work”: Union Leadership in Perilous Times. *Karla Hernández-Mats, American Federation of Teachers*

Civics Education in Real Time: Multiracial Coalition-Building for the Public Good. *Jessica Marshall, Spencer Foundation*

Chair: *Elizabeth Todd-Breland, University of Illinois at Chicago*

Discussant: *Elizabeth Todd-Breland, University of Illinois at Chicago*

58.029. A Window of Opportunity: Building an Ethnic Studies Dual Enrollment Program in Pomona, CA. Division G - Social Context of Education; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 402A;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

A Research Informed Vision for an Ethnic Studies Dual Enrollment Program Collaboration. *S. Terri Gomez, California Polytechnic State University*
Building and Sustaining Trust: Ethnic Studies Professional Development and Teacher Training. *José Manuel Aguilar-Hernández, California State Polytechnic University - Pomona*

Ethnic Studies High School Teacher Reflections on Pedagogy, Curriculum, and Impact. *Arturo Molina, Pomona Unified School District; Rita Torres; Rene Ubom, Pomona Unified School District*

Chair: *Cleveland Hayes, Indiana University - Indianapolis*

Discussant: *Cati V. de los Rios, University of California - Berkeley*

58.030. Blackness & Immigration in the Era of ICE. Division G - Social Context of Education; Workshop
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 511C;
3:45-5:15pm

Chair: *Chonika Coleman-King, University of Florida*

Participants: *Patriann Smith, University of South Florida; Takeshia Pierre, Tufts University; Thacher Tracion Loutin, University of Florida; L. Clara Mabour, Tufts University; Neisha Terry Young, Stony Brook University - SUNY*

58.031. Frameworks for STEM Equity in a Time of Polycrisis: Navigating Tensions in Theory, Practice, and Policy. Division G - Social Context of Education; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 301B;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

“I Was Told I Was Too Bubbly”: Equity Expansions Through a Virtual Geosciences Educator Network. *Karis Michelle Jones, Baylor University; Monica L. Miles, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Danielle Emeny, SUNY - Upstate Medical University; Aimee Lennox, Empire State University - SUNY; Melody Lindsay, Bigelow; Nadia Harvieux, Finger Lakes Institute; Amy Sheldon, SUNY - Geneseo*

Black Women Geoscientists in Post Secondary Education – Exploring the Intersectional Impacts of Disciplinary Curriculum. *Nicollette Mitchell, Vanderbilt University*
Stories-To-Live-By: Growing Teacher Literacies Amidst Polycrisis. *Alexandra Panos, University of South Florida; Kristin Valle Geren, University of South Florida; Jarod Roselló, University of South Florida; Mieke Valk, Polk County Schools*

Teachers in turbulent times: Mentorship, mindfulness, and meditations from early-career STEM teacher-leaders. *Caitlin M. Donovan, Duke University; Akanke Mason-Hogans, Riverside High School; Anik Sen, Riverside High School; Bre Anna Clinkscales, Jordan High School*

Learning That Grounds Us: STEM Practices for Stability and Growth. *Valencia Hicks-Harris, Duke University*

Chair: *Danielle Emeny, SUNY - Upstate Medical University*

Discussant: *Monica L. Miles, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

58.032. Global Politics, Educational Self-Determination, and Intergenerational Learning in the Iranian Diaspora. Division G - Social Context of Education; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 504;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Researching Iranian Diasporic Education: Reflections on Political and Generational Dynamics in the U.S. *Roozbeh Shirazi, University of Minnesota*

Parenting Toward Belonging to the Not-Yet-There: Identity and Imagination in Iranian Immigrant Families. *Fatemeh Hajnaghizadeh, Northwestern University*

Desire, Language, and Legacy: Iranian Parents Reimagining Bilingual Futures Amid Sociopolitical Tensions. *Yalda M. Kaveh, Arizona State University; Sepide Pazhouhi, Arizona State University; Roya Fathalizadeh, Arizona State University*

Family Pedagogies and Intergenerational Learning on the Iranian Left. *Shirin Vossoughi, Northwestern University; Mahdi Ganjavi, University of Toronto; Fatemeh Hajnaghizadeh, Northwestern University*

Chair: *Pooneh Sabouri, Florida International University*

Discussants: *Milad Mohebbali, University of Nebraska - Lincoln; Sanaz Farhangi, LeanLab Education*

58.033. Towards Altermundos: Racial Literacies and Racial Sense-Making of Latinx/e/o/a, Indigenous, Latin American-Origin Youth. Division G - Social Context of Education; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 303A;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Bilingual Education Reinforcing Latinx as a Racialized Group. *Laura Chavez-Moreno, University of California - Los Angeles*

Naming and Navigating Racism: Latinx Students Racial Literacies via Ethnic Studies. *Arturo Nevárez, California State University - Stanislaus*

Transnational Racial Literacies of Recently-Arrived Latin American and Indigenous Migrant Youth. *Rita Kamani-Renedo, Stanford University*

Oaxaqueño is Not a Bad Word: Racial Sense-Making and Resistance. *David W. Barillas Chón, University of Northern Colorado*

“Español Con Libertad”: Community-Based Organizations Fostering Racialized Social Ties for Latinx Immigrant Youth. *Sophia Rodriguez, New York University; Melissa Ortiz, New York University*

Chair: *Rita Kamani-Renedo, Stanford University*

Discussant: *Danny C. Martinez, University of California - Davis*

58.034. From the Coast to the Heartland: Scaling Integrated Student Support Systems in the Post-Pandemic Era.

Division H - Research, Evaluation and Assessment in Schools; Symposium
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 7th Floor,
Hollywood Ballroom I; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Narrowing the Achievement Gap Through Integrated Student Support: Evidence From City Connects in the Heartland. *Haibin Jiang, Boston College; Illia Polovnikov, Boston College; Eric Dearing, Boston College; Mary Elizabeth Walsh, Boston College*

Re-engaging Students: The Impact of City Connects on Attendance in a Midwestern State. *Yan Leigh, Boston College; Haibin Jiang, Boston College; Mary Elizabeth Walsh, Boston College*

Evolving Leadership Perspectives on Integrated Student Support Implementation: Insights from a Midwestern Context. *Nan Yang, Boston College; Kaylena Mann, Boston College; Red Paulin, University of Wisconsin-Madison*

Adapting Integrated Student Support for Rural Schools: A Case Study of Community-Driven Implementation. *Jee Hun Yoo, Boston College; Kathleen Trong Drucker, Boston College*

Chair: *Deoksoon Kim, Boston College*

Discussant: *Robert Behning, Marian University*

58.035. Enhancing Professional Inclusivity in Interprofessional Continuing Education Environments in the Health Professions. Division I - Education in the Professions;

Symposium

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Atrium II;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

The Evolution and Importance of Interprofessionalism in Healthcare. *Goetz Fabry, University of Freiburg*

Conceptual Frameworks for the Study of Interprofessional Learning - Exploring Current Approaches and the novel Construct "Professional Inclusivity". *Maura Polansky, University of Illinois at Chicago*

Insights and Tools from the Social Sciences to Support Future Research in Interprofessional Learning. *Nicole Perez, University of Illinois at Chicago*

Chair: *Toni Ungaretti, Johns Hopkins University*

Discussant: *Toni Ungaretti, Johns Hopkins University*

58.036. Critical considerations for in-person and online teaching. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum H; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Biology Instructors' Frames Regarding the Nature of Science: Connections to Teaching Practices and Implications. *Yoon Ha Choi, Digital Promise; Antonio Duran, Arizona State University; J. Audra Williams, Arizona State University; Aramati Casper, Colorado State University; Sarah L. Eddy,*

University of Minnesota

Bringing the Body into Online Learning with Art. *Shannon McManimon, Viterbo University; Lauren Mark, SUNY - New Paltz*

University Professors' Noticing of Diversity, Equity, Inclusion, Justice, and Accessibility in the Classroom. *Vandana Thadani, Loyola Marymount University; Zoe Katz, Loyola Marymount University; Adelaide Battin, Loyola Marymount University; Christjin R. Bell, Loyola Marymount University; Rebecca R. Michelson, Loyola Marymount University*

When the World Went Remote: A Turning Point for Accessibility in Postsecondary Education. *Desirée Lama, University of Texas at Austin; Soren Aldaco, University of Texas at Austin; Stephanie W. Cawthon, University of Texas at Austin; Ifeoluwa Adekoya, University of Texas at Austin*

On "Good" Teaching: A Scoping Review of Research University Instructors' Pedagogical Purposes, Philosophies & Practices. *Justin A. Gutzwa, Michigan State University; Damani K. White-Lewis, University of Pennsylvania; Annie M. Wofford, Florida State University; Noemi Fernandez, University of Pennsylvania; Saryu Sanghani, University of Pennsylvania; Ivana Marshall, University of Pennsylvania; May Truong, University of Pennsylvania; Catherine L. Zhang, University of Pennsylvania*

Chair: *Jonggeun Park, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Discussant: *Halkano Michael Hargura, Texas Tech University*

58.037. Impact of power and politics in higher education.

Division J - Postsecondary Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum F;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

"Existing Makes Me Political": Latino College Students' Everyday Political Acts and Imagined Futures. *Giovanna Itzel, University of California - Irvine*

Talking Politics: How Student-Faculty Dynamics Shape Political Discourse. *Jiaqi Hu, University of Massachusetts Amherst; Musbah Shaheen, University of Massachusetts - Amherst*

The Structural, Political, and Representational Oppression Shaping First-Generation Doctoral Students of Color's Imposter Phenomenon Experiences. *Ngoc Tran, University of California - Los Angeles*

Are We Satisfied with Diversity Yet? A Replication and Extension of Park's (2009) Demographic Diversity Satisfaction Study. *John Yang, UCLA; Gabriel Lê Espiritu, University of California - Los Angeles; Mitchell J. Chang, University of California - Los Angeles*

58.038. Institutional Supports that Matter: Examining Coaching, Microgrants, and Pathways to College Completion. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum

G; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Exploring the Experiences of Former College Students Who Left Without Completing a Degree. *Brendon M. Soltis, Michigan State University; Kay Stevens, Michigan State University*

Beyond Definitional Chaos: Establishing Conceptual Clarity for Academic Coaching in Higher Education. *Lauren Bagdy, University of Georgia; Hannah England, University of Georgia*

The Directed Dream: Rethinking How Advising Relates to Student Success at a California Community College. *Hoyun Kim, University of California - Berkeley*

Money Matters: University Microgrants Improve Academic Success. *Katharine Broton, University of Iowa; Solomon Fenton-Miller, University of Iowa; Nicholas A. Bowman, University of Iowa*

Chair: *Jeff Ching-Fan Lai, University of Iowa*

Discussant: *Lijing Yang, Ohio University*

58.039. Developing Preservice Teachers' Professional Noticing: Preservice Teachers' Noticing Across Diverse Contexts.

Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 8; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Asset-based Perspectives of Students and Marginalized Groups: Secondary Preservice Teachers' Noticing for Equity and Culturally Relevant Caring. *Paul J. Weinberg, Oakland University; Amber S. Bismack, Oakland University*

Characterizing Pre-service Teachers' Noticing in IT Education. *Jingxian Wang, Southwest University; Xinyan Yang, Southwest University; Zihan Huang, Southwest University*

Pre-Service Teachers Noticing and Interpreting Culturally Grounded Pedagogy in the Elementary Science Classroom. *Lauren Barth-Cohen, University of Utah; Angela Warnock, University of Utah; Tracy Dobie, University of Utah; Connor Warner, University of Utah; Bailey N. Ondricek, University of Utah; Liza Romina Escobar, University of Utah; Lynne Zummo, University of Utah*

Where's the STEM? Preservice Teachers' Noticing of STEM Learning Opportunities in Early Childhood Classrooms. *Robyn K. Pinilla, University of Texas - El Paso; Enrique Pineda Sanchez, University of Texas - El Paso; Cynthia Arraya Wiltshire, University of Texas - El Paso*

Creating Learning Opportunities for Teacher Candidates to Build Noticing Skills and Self-Efficacy with Classroom Environment. *Casedy A. Thomas, Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University; Rose Sebastian, University of Virginia*

Chairs: *Tara Barnhart, Chapman University; Keirah Comstock, University of Rochester*

Discussant: *Miray Tekkumru-Kisa, RAND Corporation*

58.040. Examining the Impact of Virtual and Video-Based PD on Teacher Growth. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 9; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

A meta-analysis of video-viewing as teacher professional development: Impact on student achievement. *Pengjin Wang, University of Hong Kong; Kexin Li, University of Hong Kong; Gaowei Chen, University of Hong Kong*

Shifts in the Analytic Stance of Noticing: How Teachers Articulate What They Notice When Viewing Ambitious Teaching. *Julie M. Amador, University of Idaho; Ryan Gillespie, University of Idaho*

Video Annotations as Professional Learning Tools: Examining Content and Form Across Annotator Roles. *D'Anna Pynes, University of Notre Dame; Michael Szopiak, University of Notre Dame*

Virtual Educator Affinity Spaces as Professional Development and An Opportunity for Adult Learner Empowerment. *Mia H. Kirk, Montclair State University*

Chair: *Gabriela López, Stanford University*

Discussant: *Saili S. Kulkarni, San Jose State University*

58.041. Racial Identity & Teacher Education: Critical Conversations about Privilege and Power. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 7; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Novice Teachers of Color Fighting to Embody Racial Literacy in Racialized Secondary School Contexts. *Corinna D. Ott, University of California - Riverside*

Pushback, performance, praxis: A critical race discourse analysis of preservice teachers' reflections on race & power. *Kyle L. Chong, Michigan State University; Travon Jefferson, Michigan State University; Candace L. Moore, Michigan State University; Taneya Chavis, Michigan State University; Terrance Burgess, Michigan State University; Terry K. Flenbaugh, Michigan State University; Maliyah H Drain, Michigan State University; Savannah Smith, John Jay College of Criminal Justice*

Whiteness in the Stories Teachers Tell: An Analysis of Pre-Service Teachers' Motivations. *Francisco Villa, Temple University; MG Hodge, Temple University; Timothy Patterson, Temple University; Abby Reisman, University of Pennsylvania*

Who are we talking about?: Reviewing Literature on Racial Identity Development in Teacher Education. *Adina Goldstein, University of Pennsylvania; Lisette N. Enumah, University of Pennsylvania; Brooke Porter, University of Pennsylvania*

Chair: *Khalilah Odessa Ali, Spelman College*

Discussant: *Zachary A. Casey, Rhodes College*

58.042. Reimagining Pedagogy: Teacher Agency, Spiritual Inclusion, and Community-Centered Education. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 6;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Insights from Radical Ethnic Studies: Creating Educational Spaces in Support of Student Holistic Ways of Being. *Christine Vega, San Jose State University; Marcos Pizarro, California State University - Los Angeles*
Veiled Pedagogy : How Spirituality and Religion Affect the Classroom Space. *Saughar Nojan, San Jose State University*
“Love, Study, Struggle”: Fugitive Pedagogy in An Asian American Studies Classroom. *Lawrence Lan, San Jose State University*

“Beyond These Campus Walls: Building & Expanding the Bulosan Center Internship Program Beyond the University”.
Wayne Jopanda, University of California - Davis

Chair: *Saughar Nojan, San Jose State University*

Discussant: *Marcos Pizarro, California State University - Los Angeles*

58.043. Division L Vice Presidential Session: The Politics of Possibility: Advancing Educational Equity for the Social Good. Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
3:45-5:15pm

Chair: *Ann LoBue, Teachers College, Columbia University*
Participants: *Sonya Douglass, Teachers College, Columbia University; Ezekiel J. Dixon-Roman, Teachers College, Columbia University; Peggy G. Carr, National Center for Education Statistics, IES; Pedro A. Noguera, University of Southern California; Carrie Sampson, Arizona State University; Jonathan E. Collins, Teachers College, Columbia University; Linda Darling-Hammond, Learning Policy Institute*

Discussant: *Janelle T. Scott, University of California - Berkeley*

58.044. Educational Battles and Bridges: Media, Curriculum, and Civic Engagement Across Contexts. Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 10; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

The Science of Reading Spectacle: A qualitative media analysis of media reporting on Science of Reading policy. *Sarah L. Woulfin, University of Texas at Austin; Daniel Dawer, University of Texas at Austin*
Control of the Curriculum in East Jerusalem: The Struggle Between Authorities Over the Educational Content. *Samira Alayan, Hebrew University of Jerusalem and David Yellin*

College of Education

Reclaiming Silenced Voices: Heritage Language Education in a Monolingual Nation-State. *Nevin Durmaz, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Teachers’ Perspectives on Curriculum Impact: Supporting Student Success Within and Beyond the Juvenile Justice System. *Emily McConaughy, University of South Florida - St. Petersburg; Allahon Marbra, University of South Florida*

What Unites and Divides U.S. Public Opinion Concerning the Goals of Civics Education. *Brandon Harrison, University of Pennsylvania; Huma Rasheed, University of Pennsylvania; Lance Holbert, University of Pennsylvania*

Chair: *Priya Goel, California State University - Dominguez Hills*

Discussant: *Nisha Acharya Julien, Opportunity Consulting*

58.045. How Technology Shapes Educational Opportunity: Promise and Pitfalls. Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 1;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Did Broadband Internet Expansion Harm Student Achievement? Examining the Affordable Connectivity Program During the Pandemic. *Nicolas Pardo, University of Southern California; Jared Nathan Schachner, University of Southern California; Hernan Galperin, University of Southern California; Francois Bar, University of Southern California*

Research on the Impact of the Digital Economy on Educational Equity: Evidence from China. *Bingjie Liu, East China Normal University*

The Allure of a Technological Solve: Hybrid Schedules for High School Students Dealing With Multiple Institutional Failures. *Brett Gardiner Murphy, Graduate Center - CUNY*

The Unequal Impact of Virtual Learning: Evidence from U.S. School Districts During COVID-19. *Paloma Lu, Boston University*

Unveiling Educational Inequity Pathways: A Causal Machine Learning Analysis of Australian Mathematics Achievement. *Hui Tao, University of Adelaide; Ruoxin Wang, University of South Australia; Haiyao Cao, University of Adelaide; Jinan Zou, University of Adelaide*

Chair: *Jie Lin, Shanghai Jiao Tong University*

Discussant: *Niu Gao, American Institutes for Research*

SIG Sessions

58.046. Advancing Equity and Effectiveness in Teacher Preparation: Insights on Accreditation, Reflection, and Reform. SIG-Accreditation, Assessment, and Program Evaluation in Education Preparation; Paper Session
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Los Feliz; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Accreditation as a Lever for Equity: Examining the Role of Educator Preparation Accreditation as a Justice-Oriented Tool. *Todd McCardle, Eastern Kentucky University; Jilliane McCardle, Eastern Kentucky University*

Novice Teachers' Perceptions of Effective Literacy Instruction Following Science of Reading Legislation. *Carla Lynn Tanguay, Georgia State University; Ruchi Bhatnagar, Georgia State University; Joyce E. Many, Georgia State University*

Making the Implicit Explicit: A Theory-Informed Reflection on Emergent Evaluation Capacity Building Practice. *Doreen Akinyi Otieno, Ohio University; Krisanna L. Machtmes, Ohio University*

A Planning Self-Perception Scale For Preservice Teachers: Content Validation And Exploratory Factor Structure. *Jennifer Stefania Herrera Lozano, University of Texas - El Paso; Erika L. Mein, University of Texas - El Paso*

Chair: *Patrick Obot, University of Houston*

Discussant: *Connor Warner, University of Utah*

58.047. Emotion, Imagination, and Engagement: Affective Elements of Adults' Digital Practices. SIG-Adult Literacy and Adult Education; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, San Gabriel A; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Emotion as Engagement: Understanding Adult Learners' Emotional Openness and Persistence in AI-Mediated Learning. *Lingfei Luan, University of Minnesota; Xi Lin, East Carolina University; Yan Dai, Tuskegee University*

Imagining Futures and Constructing Educational Pathways: Refugee Parents' Digital Literacy and Technology Integration. *Hamid Nadir, University of North Carolina - Greensboro; Joy Birabwa, University of North Carolina - Greensboro; Rachel J. Boit, University of North Carolina - Greensboro; Sudha Shreeniwas, University of North Carolina - Greensboro; Linda Hestenes, University of North Carolina - Greensboro*

Sustainable Digital Literacy Education for Older Adults and Healthy Aging. *Hyewon Park, University of California - Davis; Jieun You, Valdosta State University; Jeongsan Hwang, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Boram Yu, Yonsei University*

To Click or Not to Click: Understanding Online Trust and Risk Perception in Older Adults. *Merve Basdogan, Texas Tech University*

What Older Adults Want to Learn and How: Learning Preferences and Self-Efficacy in Digital Technology. *Sihan Jian, Florida State University; Vanessa Dennen, Florida State University*

Chair: *Oscar A. Aliaga, University of South Florida*

Discussant: *Oscar A. Aliaga, University of South Florida*

58.048. Towards a Meaningful Practice of Transparency in Arts-Based Educational Research: Structured Poster Session. SIG-Arts and Inquiry in the Visual and Performing Arts in Education; Structured Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 515B; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

1. What Colombia Taught Me: A Journey in Photographs and Memos (Poster 1). *Turan Ahmadova, University of South Florida - Tampa*
2. Stage Directions as the Scholar-Artist's Reflective and Analytic Tool (Poster 2). *Emil Asanov, Florida State University*
3. "She told me, 'This is your career. This is your craft'" : Spoken-Word Performance of Interviews with Male Los Angeles Teacher Candidates (Poster 3). *Agustin Cervantes, Bay Area K-16 Collaborative*
4. Soul Sista: Trials And Triumphs Told Through Her Eyes, Words, And Moves... (Poster 4). *Marquis B. Holley, University of South Florida*
5. Centering Storytelling, Improvisation, and Sensory Phenomena in Choreographic Interviews (Poster 5). *Lindsay Lindberg, University of California - Los Angeles*
6. Emergent Bilinguals' Experiences of Escaping Social Anxiety with Improv Theater (Poster 6). *David Metz, Los Angeles Unified School District*
7. Facets of Transparency in Musical Arts-Based Education Research (Poster 7). *Amanda Odom, University of South Florida - Tampa*
8. Exploring Local Cartographies of Institutional Practice: Mapping Transparency, Discourses, and Impact Literacies in Art as Research (Poster 8). *Pei-Jung Tsai, University of British Columbia; Anita Sinner, University of British Columbia*
9. To Score or Not to Score: That is the Ethical Question (Poster 9). *Joseph Salvatore, New York University*
10. Tensions and Questions on Engaging Ethnodramatic Performers in a University Setting (Poster 10). *Charles F. Vanover, University of South Florida*
11. Documentary Theatre as Lived Memory: An Autoethnographic Approach to Historical Atmosphere (Poster 11). *Daria Vystavkina, Cologne-Bonn Academy in Exile*
12. Rootedness, Uprootedness and Rootlessness (Poster 12). *Botao Wu, University of British Columbia*

Chair: *Charles F. Vanover, University of South Florida*

Discussant: *Jaime Fiddler, University of Calgary*

58.049. Reading Otherwise: Centering Shared Selves and Collective Knowing in Asian American Youth Adult Literature. SIG-Asian Americans and Pacific Islanders in Education and Research; Working Group Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 501A; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Understanding Filipino American Identities Through Kapwa.
Eric Claravall, California State University - Sacramento;
Elizabeth Isidro, Western Michigan University

‘정’ (Jeong) as a Means to Explore Character Positioning in
Finding Junie Kim. *Monica S. Yoo, University of Colorado -*
Colorado Springs; Kwangok Song, University of Kansas

远亲不如近邻: Identity-Seeking Journey in Maizy Chen’s Last
Chance. *Shuling Yang, University of Maryland - Baltimore*
County

Chair: *Monica S. Yoo, University of Colorado - Colorado Springs*

**58.050. The Science of Reading Through a Multilingual Lens:
Critical Perspectives from Teacher Education to Policy.**

SIG-Bilingual Education Research; Symposium

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304B;

3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Science of Reading in Dual Language Education Context in
Utah. *Tuba Yilmaz, University of Utah; Ellie T. Akerley,*
University of Utah

Emancipatory Literacies Resisting Structured Literacy
Mandates: Teacher Educators Advocating for New Mexico’s
Multilingual Communities. *Jen Stacy, University of New*
Mexico; Mary F. Rice, University of New Mexico; Sepideh
Yasrebi, University of New Mexico; Joshua T. Frank
Cárdenas, University of New Mexico; Violet Henderson,
New Mexico State University; Adrian Sandoval, University
of North Dakota; Daniel Olufemi, University of New Mexico;
Rosalia Pacheco, University of New Mexico; Dawn Berry,
New Mexico Highlands University

Disrupting the Science of Reading Through Family-Based
Multilingual Research: Preservice Teachers as
Ethnographers of Literacy. *Jungmin Lee, University of*
Louisiana at Lafayette; Min-Seok Choi, University of
Louisiana at Lafayette

Chair: *Ellie T. Akerley, University of Utah*

Discussant: *Ester J. de Jong, University of Colorado - Denver*

**58.051. Transnational Perspectives: International Teachers
Advancing Bilingualism & Inclusive Education Amid
Teacher Shortages.** SIG-Bilingual Education Research;

Symposium

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 506;

3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Centering Transnational Knowledge: International Visiting
Teachers in Oregon Dual Language Bilingual Education
Classrooms. *Soria E. Colomer, Oregon State University;*
Nelly N. Patiño-Cabrera, Oregon State University; Amanda
Kibler, Oregon State University; Vanessa Mejia-Hutchison,
Oregon State University; Colin Cole, Independent Scholar
The Lived Experiences of International Dual

Language/Immersion Teachers in North Carolina. *Nicolette*
Grant, University of North Carolina - Charlotte

Reconstructing Agency for Inclusion: Two Chinese
International Teachers’ Experiences with Disability in Dual
Language Classrooms. *Lingyu Li, Lehman College - CUNY*

Transnational Teacher Education for Inclusive Education:

German Preservice Teachers’ Perspectives. *Wiebke J.*

Langer, University of Hamburg; Doris A. Kroiss, University
of North Carolina - Greensboro; Ye He, University of North
Carolina - Greensboro

Chair: *Soria E. Colomer, Oregon State University*

Discussant: *Socorro Herrera, Kansas State University*

**58.052. Examining the Experiences of Career and Technical
Education Teachers and Workforce Professionals.** SIG-

Career & Technical Education and Workplace Learning;

Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum E;

3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

“It Made It Very Real”: Awe as a Source of Meaning for
Workforce Development Professionals. *Megan Powell*
Cuzzolino, Harvard University; Jeffrey Bachman, Harvard
University

Strengthening Instructional Leadership Skills of Regional,
Shared-time Center Directors: Testing a Leadership
Academy model. *James R. Stone, Southern Regional*
Education Board; Lisa Shannon, Magnolia Consulting, LLC.

Motivations and Experiences of High School IT Teachers in the
U.S.: A Mixed Methods Study. *Kelli M. Adam, Texas A&M*
University; Trina J. Davis, Texas A&M University

Make It Make Sense: What Veteran SBAE Teachers Reveal
About Policy, Practice and Professional Agency. *Demikia*
Taylor, Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University;
Tiffany Drape, Virginia Tech

Chair: *Michelle E. Bartlett, Old Dominion University*

58.053. Critical Curriculum Issues in Higher Education:

Access and Teacher Preparation. SIG-Critical Issues in

Curriculum and Cultural Studies; Paper Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304C;

3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

“It’s Giving Conditional Accept”: The Role of Whiteness in
First-Year College Success Courses. *Janelle Grant-*
Ashbaugh, Grand Valley State University

Mobilities, Equity, and the Higher Education Curriculum. *S.*
Otto Khera, New Mexico State University

Normalistas-teachers offering epistemic feminisms from the
Global South. *Raul Olmo Fregoso Bailón, University of*
Nevada - Reno

Unforgetting Justice in Teacher Preparation: A Curriculum
Analysis for Equity and Futuring. *Asli Neriman Ogulcuklu*
Cevik, Pennsylvania State University

Using Fictionalization to (Re)Calibrate: Integrating Theoretical Frameworks for Literacy and Liberation. *Tierney B Hinman, Auburn University; Wendy L. Gardiner, Pacific Lutheran University; Amy Leigh Tondreau, University of Maryland - Baltimore County*

58.054. Unforgetting Histories and Imagining Futures in Early Childhood Teacher Education. SIG-Critical Perspectives on Early Childhood Education; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 401;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Engaging In-Service Early Childhood Educators in Collaborative Inquiry: Challenging One-Size-Fits-All Professional Development. *Meilan Jin, Western Washington University; Margarita Ruiz, Western Washington University*

From Shortage to Sustainability: Transforming ECSE Teacher Preparation through Project Camino. *Abigail Akosua Amoako Kayser, James Madison University; Aja McKee, California State University, Fullerton; Janice Myck-Wayne, California State University - Fullerton; Rosario M. Ordonez-Jasis, California State University - Fullerton*

"If I Leave, Who Stays?" A Narrative Inquiry of Early Childhood Educators' Attrition Decisions. *Lucie Cyliax, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Stephanie C. Sanders-Smith, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Mandated Methods, Missing Culture: Reimagining Structured Literacy in Early Childhood Teacher Education. *Angela Kollerer, San Francisco State University*

No Path Without Us: Reclaiming Early Educator Voice in the Future of California's UPK Reform. *Sarah Elisa Stein, San Francisco State University; Mina Kim, San Francisco State University*

Discussant: *Kerry H. Alexander, University of Maryland*

58.055. Generative Difference and More-Than-Human Educational Worldings. SIG-Critical Posthuman and Postfoundational Studies in Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum D; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Crippled Bodyminds as Posthuman: Echolalia and Non-Verbality in Educational Worlding. *Brad Bierdz, Georgia Southern University*

Envisioning Educational Futures Through a Speculative Fiction Children's Story. *Emma Minke McMains, University of Arkansas; Kaleb Bass, Independent Scholar*

Ink and Flesh: Tattoos as Collaborative Palimpsests of Trauma and Posthuman Literacy. *Tori K. Flint, University of Louisiana at Lafayette; Heather N. Stone, University of Louisiana at Lafayette*

Muchness, Normalization, and Montessori Theory: Tensions and Possibilities in Reinterpreting Developmental Frameworks for a Postdevelopmental Early Childhood

Future. *Ginger Mayhew, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Neurocurious Research-Creation: Performing Educational Possibilities Beyond Neurotypical/Neurodivergent Binaries. *Meaghan Krazinski, Curry College*

Chair: *Laura M. Jewett, University of Texas - Rio Grande Valley*

Discussant: *Richard V. Kahn, Antioch University*

58.056. Democratic Citizenship in Education Business Meeting. SIG-Democratic Citizenship in Education; Business Meeting
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Atrium I;
3:45-5:15pm

Chair: *Ellen Middaugh, San Jose State University*

Discussant: *Hillary Parkhouse, Virginia Commonwealth University*

58.057. Innovative Design for Learning and Human Flourishing. SIG-Design and Technology; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Santa Barbara C; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

An Educational Design Research Journey through Space: Gamifying an Instructional Design Course. *Susie Gronseth, University of Houston; Sara G. McNeil, University of Houston*

Bridging Math and Machine Learning through Concreteness-Fading and Generative AI Tools. *Hyunju Oh, University of Florida; Rui Guo, University of Florida; Chenglu Li, University of Utah*

Enhancing Cleanroom Readiness: Design and Evaluation of Photolithography Procedure Training in Immersive Virtual Reality. *Shangman Li, University of Missouri; Hao He, Emporia State University; Xinhao Xu, University of Missouri; Fang Wang, University of Missouri; Sura Muhsin, University of Missouri; Mahmoud Almasri, University of Missouri; Yuanyuan Gu, University of Missouri*

From Collaboration to Creation: Co-Designing Personalized Learning Technologies for Inclusive Music Classrooms. *Tiffany Anne Roman, Kennesaw State University; Erin E Collins, Cobb County School District*

From Values to Practice: Co-Designing an AI Evaluation Framework with K-12 Teachers. *Melika Ziba, Iowa State University; Evrim Baran, Iowa State University; Melis Dilek, Iowa State University*

Chair: *Md Mamunur Rashid, University of Rochester*

Discussant: *Salih Mansur, Touro University*

58.058. Deweyan Responses to Authoritarianism, Artificial Intelligence, and Threats to Democratic Education. SIG-Dewey Studies; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 303B;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Dewey and the Machine: Democracy and Education in the Age of AI. *Nick DePascal, University of New Mexico*
Intelligence and the Anti-Democratic Threat of the Authoritarian Right: A Deweyan Response. *Austin J. Pickup, Aurora University; Jessica Heybach, Western Michigan University*
Pragmatic Disalienation: A Fanonian Intervention into Deweyan Pragmatism. *Ryland Frost, Williamsburg Charter High School*
Transnational Deweyans: African Intellectuals and the Making of Progressive Education for Nation-Building. *Toyosi Stephen Adedara, Baylor University*
Virtuous Foundations: Reconstructing Democratic Agency Through Phronesis and Basic Goods in an Age of Algorithmic Authoritarianism. *Sean Chen Liu, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University*
Chair: *Charles L. Lowery, Virginia Tech*

58.059. Emotions, identities, and engagement in climate change education. SIG-Environmental Education; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 404AB;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Digital Platforms for Climate Education: A Participatory Mapping Study of Use and Impact. *Victoria Desimoni, Arizona State University; Andrea E. Weinberg, Arizona State University; Iveta Silova, Arizona State University; Michelle Jordan, Arizona State University*

Emotional Drivers of Climate Action in Taiwan: Implications for Lifelong and Adult Climate Change Education. *Yu-Chi Tseng, National Taiwan Normal University; Yen-Chun Ross Lin, National Taiwan Normal University*

Environmental Literacy as a Catalyst for Civic Engagement and Climate Action Among University Students: A Cross-National Inquiry. *Marika Rullo, university of siena; Erica Molinario, Florida Gulf Coast University; Giovanni Telesca, Università degli Studi di Modena e Reggio Emilia; Claudio Melacarne, University of Siena; Claudia Banchetti, Università di Siena*

Geopolitical Shifts in Male Gender Socialization and Implications for Climate Change Education. *Joseph A. Henderson, University of Vermont; David E. Long, Morehead State University; Antti J. Rajala, University of Eastern Finland; Jonas Greve Lysgaard, Aarhus University - School of Education; Pasha Dashtgard, American University; Paula Sophie Betancourt, Aarhus University - School of Education*

Youth Climate Engagement Through Head, Heart, and Hands: A Qualitative Study in New York City. *Renda Sun, Teachers College, Columbia University; Felicia Moore Mensah, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Chair: *Tatiana Chelle Height, University of North Carolina - Charlotte*

Discussant: *Alexandra Schindel, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

58.060. Constructing New Visions in K-12 School Finance: The Past, Present, and Future of State Interventions into District Finances. SIG-Fiscal Issues, Policy and Education Finance; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 3;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

School Debt Under Fiscal Surveillance: A Policy Analysis of State Audits of California Districts. *René Espinoza Kissell, University of California - Santa Cruz*

Community Education and Resistance to State Takeover: Bridging Local and State Struggles. *Yaritza Gonzalez, ING Rising*

The "Side Effects" of K-12 Fiscal Accountability Policy. *Christopher Saldaña, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Laura Davalos, Wisconsin Center for Education Research*
The Possibility of Green Fiscal Mutualism in California. *David Isaac Backer, Seton Hall University; Mia Fullerton, Reed College*

Chair: *Daniel Espinoza, University of Southern California*

Discussant: *Erica O. Turner, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

58.061. Pathways to Possibility: Equity, Identity, & Career Pathways. SIG-Graduate and Postdoctoral Education across the Disciplines; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 2;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Career Pathways and Skill Preparedness among Biology PhDs: A Social Cognitive Career Theory Perspective. *Lechen Li, University of Florida; Jue Wu, University of Florida*
Educational and Communal Uplift Beyond Graduate School: Latina Scholar Reflections on the McNair Scholars Program. *Laura Zamudio-Orozco, Heritage University; Amy J. Nunez, Heritage University; Jereny Mendoza, University of Texas at Austin; Mikaila Leyva, Edmonds Community College*

Mapping the Landscape: Doctoral Students' Participation in and Perceptions of Professional Development Offerings. *André R. Denham, University of Alabama; Mercy Egbuikwem, University of Alabama*

Pathways Reimagined: Black Doctoral Socialization and Futuring the Professoriate. *Reginald A. Blockett, Auburn University; Walter P. Parrish, University of Maryland - Baltimore County; Candice A. Kelly, Auburn University*

Chair: *Zhongxin Zheng, The George Washington University*

Discussant: *Joshua Wallace, University of Louisville*

58.062. Groundbreaking Venue to Publish Your Manuscripts: Introduction of the Journal of Contemplative and Holistic Education (JCHE). SIG-Holistic Education; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum I;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Mission and Direction of the Journal of Contemplative and Holistic Education: A Platform for Inner Transformation and Global Healing. *Jing Lin, University of Maryland*

Business and projects: 1. Special Issue Projects at Journal of Contemplative and Holistic Education. *Hyeyoung Bang, Bowling Green State University*

Business and Projects 2. Mapping the Field: The Handbook of Contemplative and Holistic Education. *Sachi Edwards, University of Hawai'i at Manoa*

Mindful Scholarship: Contributions from the Journal of Contemplative and Holistic Education. *Deepa Srikantaiah, American University*

From New Author to Editor: Unique Perspectives and Strategies to Successfully Publish Your Work in the Journal of Contemplative Inquiry and Holistic Education. *Steven Haberin, University of Central Florida*

Chair: *Hyeyoung Bang, Bowling Green State University*

Discussant: *Jing Lin, University of Maryland*

58.063. Reclaiming Indigenous Knowledge: Decolonial and Culturally Sustaining Pedagogies for Language, Art, and Educational Sovereignty. SIG-Indigenous Peoples of the Americas; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Georgia I; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Countering Logics of Indigenous Linguistic and Cultural Excess: Rethinking Erasure in the Maya Diaspora (Yucatan-California). *Patricia Baquedano-Lopez, University of California - Berkeley*

Indigenous Invisibility: Educational Gaps Among Non-Native Environmental Decision-Makers. *Brittany Hunt, Virginia Tech; Ryan Emanuel, Duke University; David Wilkins, University of Richmond; Shelly Wilkins, Wilkins Forum, LLC*

Lyrical Sovereignty: Indigenous Language Reclamation Through Interdisciplinary Arts Education. *Ernesto Colin, Loyola Marymount University*

"Making It Work": Native and Indigenous Students as Curricular Agents in US Schools. *Kemeyawi Wahpepah, Harvard University*

The Iñupiaq "Float Coat" Song: Using Cultural Expression Pedagogy to Solve Pressing Societal Problems. *David E. K. Smith, University of Idaho*

Chair: *M. Nathan Tanner, University of Nevada - Reno*

58.064. Navigating System Level Politics for Equity and Social Justice. SIG-Leadership for Social Justice; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Level 2, Echo Park; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Designed for Equity? A Content Analysis of PK-12 Equity Director Job Descriptions. *Ishmael Miller, Arizona State University; Celina German, Arizona State University*

Intentional Leadership Actions: Equity-Focused Transformative

Leadership Practices. *Naudia Fairclough, The George Washington University; Christine W Nganga, The George Washington University*

Transformational Testimonios: Developing Multicultural District Leaders for Social Justice. *Juan Manuel Nino, University of Texas - San Antonio*

The Politics of Equity: Central Office Responses to State and Federal Pressures on Equity Policy Implementation. *Maria Del Carmen Unda, University of Texas at Austin; Jacob Navarrete, University of Texas at Austin; Estela Lopez, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Kait Ogden, University of Texas at Austin; Joshua Childs, University of Texas at Austin; Ain A. Grooms, University of Wisconsin - Madison; April L. Peters-Hawkins, University of Houston*

Chair: *Katherine Lewis, Dominican University of California*

58.065. Leadership Preparation, Change, and Organizational Conditions. SIG-Learning and Teaching in Educational Leadership; Paper Session

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Palos Verdes; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Digital Leadership as Relational Practice: Uncovering Principals' Use of Social Media to Reimagine School-Community Engagement. *Daniel Sung-Yeol Choi, California State University - Fullerton; Elizabeth Chang, California State University - Fullerton*

Facilitating the Growth of Equity-Centered Leaders in a University/District Partnership Program. *Rebecca Ann Thessin, The George Washington University; Jennifer K. Clayton, The George Washington University; Shaun D Shepard, The George Washington University; Ababayehu Aemero Tekleselassie, The George Washington University; Leslie Trimmer, The George Washington University*

Leveling Up Quantitative Methods: Game-Based Learning for Developing Practitioner-Scholars in EdD Programs. *Nicole Ralston, University of Portland; Rebecca Smith, University of Portland*

Rethinking Change: Conceptual Shifts in How Educational Leaders Understand Organizational Conditions. *NOUR ALSHAMMARI*

Chair: *Carla Finkelstein, Towson University*

58.066. AI for Higher Education Assessment. SIG-Measurement and Assessment in Higher Education; Paper Session
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 6th Floor, Broadway; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Assessing Reliability and Divergence of Human vs. AI Writing Evaluation in Chinese EFL Expository. *Ruonan Yang, The Ohio State University*

GenAI or Teacher? How Literacy Shapes Feedback Perception. *Lena Fischer, University of Twente; Mohammadreza Farrokhnia, University of Twente; Chandan Dasgupta,*

University of Twente; Omid Noroozi, Wageningen University and Research

Measuring Leadership within a Computational Psychometrics Framework: A Multi-Modal Analysis of Behavioral Traces with LLMs. *Manru Wang, Peking University; Shiqian Huang, Peking University; Xiaoting Huang, Peking University*

Measuring Student Orientation to AI-Generated Feedback in Tertiary Education: A Validation Study of the AI-FOS. *Qishuai Zhang, The Education University of Hong Kong; Lan Yang, Education University of Hong Kong*

Predicting Medical Exam Question Difficulty: Embedding, Machine Learning, and Feature Impact. *Shicong Feng, Peking University; Tianpeng Zheng, Peking University; Hao Hang, National Institute for Communicable Disease Control and Prevention of Chinese Center for Disease Control and Prevention; Jiayi Liu, Peking University; Zhehan Jiang, Peking University*

Discussant: *Youn Seon Lim, University of Cincinnati*

58.067. Evolving Issues in Education: Teacher Preparedness, Policy, and Identity. SIG-Research on Teacher Induction; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Georgia II;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Pandemic Pedagogies Reshaped the Education Landscape: A Longitudinal Study of Teacher Candidates Testimonials during COVID-19. *Gabriela Walker, National University; Rosemary Onyango*

Active Shooter Training: Perspectives of Texas Teachers. *Lizette Pacey, Texas A&M University - Kingsville; Kelly S. Hall, Texas A&M University - Kingsville*

Whose English Counts? Raciolinguistic Gatekeeping in Hiring Foreign Teachers in Thai Secondary Schools. *Piangpitcha Inthit, The Ohio State University*

Understanding the Unique Challenges in Early-Career School Librarianship. *Jenna Spiering, University of South Carolina; Jackie Biger, University of Iowa*

Chair: *Zena --, Lewis & Clark College*

Discussant: *Ketan ., University of Massachusetts - Amherst*

58.068. From Evidence to Action: Bridging Research and Practice in Educational Decision-Making (Research Use SIG Paper Session). SIG-Research Use; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, La Brea; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

CAPTURE-ing Power Dynamics: A Critical Methodological Tool for Understanding Equity in Research Use. *Lok-Sze Wong, University of North Texas; Jennifer Watling Neal, Michigan State University; Joel R. Malin, Miami University (OH); Samantha Jo Shewchuk, University of Delaware; Caitlin Farrell, University of Colorado - Boulder; Elizabeth N. Farley-Ripple, University of Delaware; Dominique Brooks, University of North Texas; Abayomi Samuel*

Abodunrin, Miami University; Brian Brutzman, Michigan State University

Beliefs, evidence, and confirmation bias. Experimental study on pre-service teachers' engagement with evidence. *Kirstin Schmidt, Karlsruhe University of Education; Florian Felix Alfons Kühlwein, Karlsruhe University of Education; Samuel Merk, Karlsruhe University of Education*

How to communicate evidence to teachers: Comparing the effects of verbal and visual effect size representation. *Florian Felix Alfons Kühlwein, Karlsruhe University of Education; Samuel Merk, Karlsruhe University of Education; Jürgen Schneider, DIPF | Leibniz Institute for Research and Information in Education; Kirstin Schmidt, Karlsruhe University of Education*

Community-Based Organizations's Use of Research Evidence to Inform State Education Policy. *Sofia Bahena, University of Texas - San Antonio*

58.069. Rooted Futures: Learner-Centered Postsecondary Models for Rural Learners. SIG-Rural Education; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum A; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Family-Centered Innovation: Integrating Indigenous Values into Student Caregiver Supports at Rural Tribal Colleges and Universities. *Theresa Anderson, The Urban Institute; Lisa Silverstein, American Indian College Fund; Jonathan Breaker, American Indian College Fund; Michael Marie Munson, Montana State University; Tiffany Gusbeth, American Indian College Fund; Elizabeth Osche, PERG Learning; Jeremi Laducer, Turtle Mountain College*

Bridging Gaps, Building Futures: Empowering Rural Paraprofessionals through Teacher Preparation Pathways. *Gloria Delany-Barmann, Western Illinois University; Carla Paciotto, Western Illinois University; Lindsay Meeker, Western Illinois University; Boh Young Lee, Western Illinois University*

Mentoring on Rural Terms: A Framework for Supporting Community College Learners. *Mayra Nuñez Martinez, University of California - Davis; Jordan Reed, University of Washington; Lia Wetzstein, University of Washington; Susannah Davis, University of Washington; Katherine M. Kovacich, University of Washington - Seattle*

Chair: *Elizabeth Kurban, American Institutes for Research*

Discussant: *Billie Jo Day, American Institutes for Research*

58.070. Multimodal Identity Work: Visual and Embodied Approaches to Critical Reflection in Teacher Education. SIG-Second Language Research; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum B; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Using Multimodal Portraits as a Path to Critical Self-Reflection

in MLL Teacher Preparation. *Yueyue Wang, University of Maryland; Golnar Fotouhi, University of Massachusetts - Lowell; Jessica B Crawford, University of Maryland; Loren Jones, University of Maryland; Johanna M. Tigert, University of Turku; Megan Madigan Peercy, University of Maryland; Melanie F. Hardy-Skeberdis, Penn State University; Daisy Fredricks, Grand Valley State University; Cesar Guitunga, University of Maryland*

Teacher Candidates' Multimodal Exploration of Emotions, Language Ideologies, and Identity at a Hispanic Serving Institution. *Kathryn I. Henderson, University of Texas - San Antonio; Bedrettin Yazan, University of Texas - San Antonio*

Mapping Language, Mapping Futures: Pre-Service Teachers Enacting Humanizing Pedagogy Through Linguistic Cartography. *Emily Phillips Galloway, Vanderbilt University; Christine Montecillo Leider, University of Massachusetts - Lowell; Christina L. Dobbs, Boston University*

From Script to Screen: Language Teacher Emotions as Discursive Resources in Multimodal Sociodramas Exploring Raciolinguistics. *Amber N. Warren, Vanderbilt University; Fares J. Karam, University of Nevada - Reno*

Chair: *Yueyue Wang, University of Maryland*

Discussant: *Matt DeRoo, Florida International University*

58.071. Investment, Inputs and Hoarding: The Role of Parents and Families on Status and Achievement. SIG-Sociology of Education; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 501C;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Education for Productivity or Positionality: Parental Inputs and Children's Academic Achievement. *XIAO YUAN, Chinese University of Hong Kong*

How Middle-Class Parents Negotiate with Their Children on Opportunity Hoarding? *Shira Klimor Maman, Bar Ilan University; Idit Fast, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev; Yariv Feniger, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev*

Mapping Parental Involvement and Engagement: A Text Network Analysis of U.S. School District Handbooks. *Angran Li, New York University - Shanghai; Zixi Chen, NYU Shanghai; Jiuyu Chen, Columbia University*

More for Boys? Gendered Effects of Parental Involvement on Math Performance in Korea. *Yijun Won, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

“Para Que Sean Mejor Que Yo”: Immigrant Parents Reimagining Status Through their Children's College Journeys. *Leslie Patricia Luqueño, Stanford University*

Chair: *Brittany C. Murray, Davidson College*

58.072. Technology and Tools Useful for Teaching Research Methods and Statistics. SIG-Teaching and Learning Research Methods; Paper Session
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Echo

Park; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Teaching Graduate Students to Use AI in Research Study Development. *Sharon H. Ulanoff, California State University - Los Angeles; Joan C. Fingon, California State University - Los Angeles; Tina Duong, San Marino Unified School District*

Navigating AI in Qualitative Research: Faculty Perspectives in the Postdigital Era. *Lorien S. Jordan, University of South Florida; Tanja S Bruxmeier, University of South Florida; Daria Smirnova, University of South Florida; Paul G. Sauberer, University of South Florida; Ethan Harris, University of Arkansas at Fayetteville; Mary Margaret Hui Cunningham, Arkansas State University*

Teaching about the Test of Symmetry. *Maria D. Vásquez-Colina, Florida Atlantic University; Mary G. Lieberman, Florida Atlantic University; John D. Morris, Florida Atlantic University*

Crosswalking Data Collection Tools: An Instructive Example of Crafting Integrative Capacity in Mixed Methods Research. *Marcia Gail Headley, University of Delaware; Haritha Malladi, University of Delaware; Pamela S. Lottero-Perdue, Towson University*

Chair: *Karen Moran Jackson, Soka University of America*

Discussant: *Megan K. Mitchell, University of Central Florida*

58.073. Examining How Teacher Thinking and Knowledge Impact History Classrooms: Studies with Preservice Teachers. SIG-Teaching History; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum J;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Examining teacher learning during Technology Assisted Lesson Study. *Jada Kohlmeier, Auburn University; Jesus Tirado, Auburn University; Matthew F. Summerlin, Auburn University; Megan Andrews, Auburn University; Terrance Joshua Lewis, University of Alabama*

Examining the Relationship Between Labor History and Critical Consciousness. *Michael A. Kreckler, Baylor University; Kevin R. Magill, Baylor University; Arturo Rodriguez, Boise State University*

“When human history fell short”: Art museums, counter-storytelling, and preservice history teacher identities. *Michael Joseph, Texas Tech University; Joanna Batt, University of Cincinnati*

Countering Brown v. Board: Examining the Wilmington Ten Using the Black Historical Consciousness Framework. *Cara Ward, University of North Carolina - Wilmington; Lisa Buchanan, Elon University; Denise M. Ousley-Exum, University of North Carolina - Wilmington; Donyell L. Roseboro, University of North Carolina - Wilmington*

Chair: *Maia G. Sheppard, University of Iowa*

Discussant: *Kristy Brugar, University of Oklahoma*

58.074. AI-Mediated Teaching and Learning Across Educational Contexts. SIG-Technology, Instruction, Cognition & Learning; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, San Gabriel B; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

How Does AI-Assisted Teaching Influence K–12 Student Learning? A Meta-Analysis of Experimental Studies. *Chen Gong, Beijing Normal University; Min Lin, Shenzhen University*

How Does GenAI Impact EFL Learners' Motivation, Emotion, and Self-Efficacy: A Meta-Analysis. *Yanyang Shen, East China Normal University; Shuzhen Chen, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Yuzhuo CHEN, East China Normal University*

Investigating the training effectiveness of a theory-driven multi-agent system for pre-service teachers' interpersonal communication competence. *Mingzi Zhang, East China Normal University; Min Lan, Zhejiang Normal University*

The Impact of Learner Characteristics and AI Utilization on Learning Experiences in a Smart Nutrition Education Platform. *Shan Li, Lehigh University; Juan Zheng, Lehigh University; Guozhu Ding, Guangzhou University*

58.075. Part 2: Celebrating the 60th Anniversary of Urban Education: Past, Present, and Future Directions. SIG-Urban Learning, Teaching, and Research; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum C; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Still Searching for a Match: Revisiting Ethnic Matching in Urban Education Through the Lens of Equity, History, and Place. *Donald Easton-Brooks, University of Nevada - Reno; Jemimah L Young, Texas A&M University; Devin Williams, University of California - Riverside*

Beyond Checklists: Applying an "I Spy" Approach to Evaluating Children's Literature in Urban Classrooms. *Cynthia A. Tyson, The Ohio State University; Ashley N. Patterson, Pennsylvania State University*

Building School–Family–Community Partnerships as Acts of Justice, Resilience, and Courage: A Justice-Centered, Resilience-Focused Framework for Urban Schools. *Julia Bryan, Pennsylvania State University*

"I want to remember who I am": Decolonizing urban school leadership through African immigrant youth schooling experiences. *Eskender A. Yousof, University of Minnesota; Muhammad Khalifa, The Ohio State University*

Reclaiming Urban Education: From Miseducation to Liberation Through Critical Race Curriculum. *Margarita Bianco, University of Colorado - Denver*

Mapping Joy, Rage and Healing: Restoring the Humanity of Twice Exceptional Urban Students. *Renae D. Mayes, University of Arizona; Riley Drake, University of Wisconsin - Stout; Benjamin Kearl, Purdue University - Fort Wayne*

Chairs: *James L. Moore, National Science Foundation; Erik Hines, George Mason University*

Discussants: *Donna Y. Ford, The Ohio State University; Tanya J Middleton, The Ohio State University*

Division and SIG Roundtables

58.076. AERA Roundtable Session Friday 3:45 pm; Roundtable Session

58.076-1. Mapping Spatial Injustice: Educational and Food Access (Table 1). Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Food Sharing, Graduate Education, and Being in the 21st Century Academy. *Michael W. Moses, University of California - Riverside; Re'Nyqua Farrington, University of California - Riverside; Katrya Txay Ly, University of California - Riverside; Edwin Leonidas Rivera Castellanos, University of California - Riverside*

From Social to Spatial Justice in Campus Food Insecurity: Equity, Access, and Futures. *Tanaporn Supanichrattana, Illinois State University; Huachen Gao, Illinois State University*

Mapping Marginalisation: The Spatial Politics of Special Needs Education. *Lucie Zundans-Fraser, Charles Sturt University*
Spatial Inequities in College Access: Mapping Non-Graduating Student Clusters and Place-Based Strategies. *Jina Kim, Johns Hopkins University*

58.076-2. Prioritizing Community Knowledge: Resistance, Re-Imagining and Reparations (Table 2). Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Across Time and Place: Storying Educational Experiences Across Cultures to Imagine Hopeful Futures for Learning. *Kevin Brown, Arizona State University; Rebekah Jongeward, Arizona State University; Bregje van Geffen, Arizona State University; Lin Yan, Arizona State University*

Expanding Avenues for Science Learning: Toward Socio-Ecological Thriving in a Mexican Immigrant-Led Community Garden. *Linnea K Beckett, Michigan State University; Michelle Hernandez Romero, University of California - Los Angeles; Samuel Severance, Northern Arizona University*

Mapping Chronic Absenteeism Risk Through a Social Context Lens across Communities. *Yung-Hui Chien, San Mateo County Office of Education; Lihua Yang, San Mateo County Office of Education; Anya Macomber, San Mateo County*

Office of Education; Jeremy Del Carpio, San Mateo County Office of Education; Leena Bhai, San Mateo County Office of Education; Jared Prolo, San Mateo County Office of Education

58.076-3. Shifting Demographics and Policy in Rural and Suburban Contexts (Table 3). Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

“It’s a Village Mentality”: Centering Community Members’ Histories and Education in a Shifting Black Suburb. *Nicole R. Misra, University of Missouri - St. Louis; Jerome E. Morris, University of Missouri - St. Louis*

Summer Brain Gains: Research on a Place-Conscious STEM and Humanities Enrichment Experience for Rural Learners. *Clint D. Whitten, Virginia Tech; Annie Shaba, Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University; Amy Price Azano, Virginia Tech*

The Browning Of America’s Suburbs: How Elementary School Teachers Are Navigating Demographic Transformation. *Meghan Phadke, Miami University (OH)*

“We Don’t Have Those Kids Here”: Localism and Multicultural Policy in a white Appalachian Head-Start. *Sung Ryung Lyu, American University; Allison Sterling Henward, Pennsylvania State University*

58.076-4. On Arts and Ethnic Studies in Educational Research (Table 4). Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Art Museums as Catalysts: Cross-Sector Collaborations in Regional Educational Ecosystems. *Wanru Zhou, Malvern College Qingdao*

La Lotería as Creative Resistance; Art Education and Ethnic Studies as Self Inquiry and Healing. *Luis Genaro Garcia, California State University - Sacramento; Roxana Daylen Dueñas, Los Angeles Unified School District*

“Tú eres mi otro yo”: Cross-Racial Learning and Solidarity at the College of Ethnic Studies. *Michael Angel Rodriguez Vázquez, Mt. San Antonio College*

Chair: *Edward R. Curammeng, California State University - Dominguez Hills*

58.076-5. Participatory Action Research for Educational Justice (Table 5). Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Fostering youth-led action: Navigating the institutional

constraints of school-based Youth Participatory Action Research. *Rosalinda Godinez, Cleveland State University; Maura Shramko, American Institutes for Research; Rose Sisay, American Institutes for Research*

Disrupting Architectures of Adulthood in Participatory Research. *Vaughn W.M. Watson, Michigan State University; Katie Tasch Bielecki, Michigan State University; Joanne E. Marciano, Michigan State University; Akinkunmi Ibrahim Oseni, Michigan State University; Sandra Boateng, Michigan State University; Beth A. Herbel-Eisenmann, Michigan State University*

Co-Writing the “Long Path” With Youth: Intergenerational Inquiry as Futuring and Civic Repair. *Jennifer Freed, University of Pennsylvania; Vivian L. Gadsden, University of Pennsylvania; Sharnita Midgett, University of Pennsylvania; Zili Zhang, Pennsylvania State University*
Chair: *Angela L. Malorni, Rutgers University*

58.076-6. Latinidad in Context (Table 6). Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

A Qualitative Study of Latine Parents’ Experiences with Common Core State Standards. *Susana Beltran-Grimm, Portland State University; Vanessa Noemy Bermudez, University of California - Irvine; Julie Salazar, University of California - Irvine; Sasha Reinwald Albrecht, Portland State University*

Exploring Newcomers Experiences using LatCrit. *Robert J. Lynn, Texas Tech University; Sara Garcia, Texas Tech University; Weverton Ataíde Pinheiro, Texas Tech University*

La Mesa Sabe Todo: Cultural Communal Pláticas as Sites of Unforgetting in Qualitative Inquiry. *Joshua Mark Anzaldúa, University of Texas - San Antonio*

Latinas in the Figured World of Economics: Creating Identity and Agency. *Cynthia Lee Gamez, El Paso Community College; Christina Convertino, University of Texas - El Paso*
Chair: *Noor Ali, Northeastern University*

58.076-7. Transforming Systems, Centering Equity: Advancing Racial Justice through Continuous Improvement (Table 7). SIG-Improvement Science in Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Democratizing Data in an Equity-focused Networked Improvement Community. *Ariel Tichnor-Wagner, Boston University; Alia Verner, EdVestors; Ruth Mercado-Zizzo, EdVestors*

Faculty use of equity-related data for continuous improvement: Findings from a new survey instrument. *Bethany Sansing-*

Helton, University of Wisconsin - Madison

Towards Continuous Improvement of a Racial Awareness and Knowledge Intervention: A Case from Michigan. *Chezare A. Warren, Vanderbilt University; Dorinda Carter Andrews, Michigan State University; Bryan Beverly, Michigan State University; Kenneth A. Frank, Michigan State University*

Transforming Outcomes for Men of Color: A Networked Improvement Community Approach. *Jesse Enriquez, California State University - Dominguez Hills; Matthew Smith, California State University - Dominguez Hills; William Franklin, California State University - Dominguez Hills*

Chair: *Katrina Struloeff, University of Pennsylvania*

58.076-8. Mentoring Pathways from K-12 to Graduate Studies (Table 8). SIG-Mentorship and Mentoring Practices; Roundtable Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Mentee Perceptions of Informal Mentoring Relationships, Well-Being, and Belonging Occurring During High School and Post-Graduation. *Amanda Ruth Duran Sunderman, American International School of Vilnius; Margaret E. Constantino, College of William & Mary; James H. Stronge, College of William & Mary; Leslie W. Grant, College of William & Mary*

“When We’re in Cogen, We Connect!”: Cogenerative Mentorship between High School Students and Scientists. *Pei-Ling Hsu, University of Texas - El Paso*

Between Access and Absence: Latino/x Men’s Search for Faculty Mentorship in Doctoral Economics. *Edgar Fidel Lopez, California State University - Northridge*

Chair: *Kathleen Mary Cowin, Washington State University - Tri-Cities*

58.076-9. Resistance, Activism And Liberatory Education (Table 9). SIG-Decolonial, Postcolonial, and Anti-Colonial Studies in Education; Roundtable Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Youth Reclaim Narratives via Environmental Justice Digital Activism and Challenge Colonizers’ Perspectives in Environmental Science. *Tasnim Aziz, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Is It Really Important to Study?: Concerning Education’s Role in the Palestine Solidarity Movement. *Jordan Corson, Stockton University*

Disrupting Oppressive Ideologies: Critical Hope in Liberatory Educators. *Steven Colmus, Texas Tech University*

Academia: The Tip of the Counterinsurgency Spear. *Jairo I. Fúnez-Flores, Independent Researcher*

58.077. AERA Roundtable Session Friday 3:45 pm - Gold 1; Roundtable Session

58.077-1. Roundtable Session 5: Student Learning and Development in College and Beyond (Table 1). Division J

- Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

An exploratory analysis of how civic online reasoning develops during college. *Enrique Eduardo Valencia Lopez, University of California - Berkeley; Jeffrey M. DeVries, University of California - Irvine*

Becoming Community Historians: What College Students Learn from Conducting Oral Histories. *Kathia Chilavert, University of Connecticut; Morgaen L. Donaldson, University of Connecticut*

Campus Climate Counts: Insights on Institutional Versus Individual Predictors of Academic AI Integrity. *Peyman Jahanbin, University of Kansas; Nancy Jo Williams, University of Kansas; Atiyeh Choobkar, University of Kansas*

Investigating U.S. Students’ Intercultural Competence Development Through a Study-abroad Program: A Longitudinal Ethnographic Study. *Jiangfeng Li, Pepperdine University; Kevin M. Wong, Pepperdine University*

58.077-2. Retention, Persistence, Outcomes (Table 2). Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Same-Generation Kinship Networks: A Familial Persistence Tool. *Cherish Shanae Golden, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

The Role of Summer Research Programs in Building Students’ Graduate School Efficacy. *Jeffrey K. Grim, George Mason University; Dianna Alvarado, University of Michigan; Cris Berry, George Mason University; Missy Fuentes Delgado, University of Michigan*

Education Interrupted: Examining the Aspirations and Academic Trajectories of Military Spouse College Students. *Carrie Carter, North Carolina State University; Latosha R. Henderson, Temple University*

A Latent Class Analysis of University Degree Trajectories Among Computer Science Transfer Students. *Kaitlyn N. Stormes, University of Georgia; Jennifer M. Blaney, University of Georgia*

Chair: *Juan Pedro Ross-Olivares, University of California - Los Angeles*

58.077-3. International Issues in Organizational Culture (Table 3). Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Placing faith in sectoral actors during Covid-19: Networked higher education governance in three cities. *Abbas Abbasov, University of Texas at El Paso*

Routine and Campaign Governance in the Restructuring and Optimization of Academic Program Structures in Chinese Higher Education. *Bowen Song, Renmin University of China*

Shi-men Organizational Culture and Academic Aspirations of Master's Degree Students: A Chain Mediation Study in China. *Jie Liu, Tsinghua University*

University Agglomeration and Research Productivity: Evidence from Cross-City Branch Campus Expansion in China. *Yulian Cao, East China Normal University; Ye Xiao, South China Normal University*

Chair: *Haishan Yang, University of Southern California*

58.077-4. Division J Section 6: Roundtable 3 (Table 4). Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Catalyzing Educational Investment: NAFTA and Higher Education in South Texas. *Erin Doran, University of Texas - El Paso; Vincent D. Carales, University of Houston*

"Policing the Racial Lines": Examining Police Engagement at Traditionally White Higher Education Institutions. *Kelly Schlabach, University of Connecticut*

Resilience and Transformation: The Pandemic's Effects on Texas Community Colleges. *Katherine Hughes, EdWordian, LLC; Holly Kosiewicz, University of Texas at Dallas; Trey Miller, University of Texas - Dallas; Arslan Khalid, University of Arkansas at Fayetteville*

Sowing Seeds: Advancing a Critical Multi-Theoretical Approach Towards Anti-Black Organizational Change in Higher Education. *Emerald Green, University of California - Berkeley*

58.077-5. Justice by Design: Humanizing STEM Education Through Equity, Culture, and Teacher Development (Table 5). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Building an Evaluation Framework for Reflection and Feedback in Culturally and Linguistically Sustaining STEM Pedagogies. *Shim Lew, University of West Florida; Ji Hye Shin, Kennesaw State University; Minkyoung Kim, University of West Florida; John L. Pecore, University of West Florida; Melissa Demetrikopoulos, Institute for Biomedical Philosophy*

Cultivating Humanizing Pedagogies: Nurturing Teachers'

Implementation of Culturally Responsive-Sustaining Education in Computer Science. *Cheri Fancsali, Research Alliance for New York City Schools; Kathryn Hill, Research Alliance for New York City Schools; Alexandra Adair, The College Board*

Developing AI Literacy Through Teacher Professional Development in STEM: Design Principles for Equitable Integration in K-12 Contexts. *Blessed Aspinas Mhungu, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

Envisioning Justice-Oriented STEM Classrooms: Preservice Teachers' SEL Beliefs, Identities, and Equity Connections. *Nelson Alejandro Ramos, California State University - Los Angeles; Sabrina Morales, California State University - Los Angeles; Sarah Manchanda, California State University - Los Angeles; Aukeem A. Ballard, University of California - Berkeley*

Knowledge of Context and Culture: Advancing Teacher Knowledge to Transform Mathematics for All. *Brian Odiwuor, Syracuse University*

Chair: *Shim Lew, University of West Florida*

58.077-6. La Frontera: Examining Issues of Educational Justice from North to South America (Table 6). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Latin American Social Justice Teacher Education: Theoretical perspectives and practical findings from regional experiences. *Catalina Cuenca, Universidad Alberto Hurtado; Mariateresa Rojas, Alberto Hurtado University*

Teaching Truth in Hostile Times: Preparing Teachers for the Fight for Ethnic Studies in K-12 Schools. *Darlene Lee, University of California - Los Angeles*

What do the identities and capitals of working-class students contribute to teacher education in Chile? *Gustavo Adolfo González, Universidad Católica Silva Henríquez; Laura Elisa Muñoz, Universidad Católica Silva Henríquez; Paulina Marcela Gamboa, Universidad Católica Silva Henríquez*

Chair: *Diane Codding, University at Albany - SUNY*

58.077-7. We Shall Not Be Moved: Honoring Identities, Motivations, and Well-Being in Teacher Preparation and Development (Table 7). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Job Satisfaction and Intent to Stay of Special Education Teachers of Color. *Shivani Oberoi, University of Washington*

Narratives of Black Residents' Motivation for Teaching and Choosing Teacher Residency Programs. *Michelle Nguyen*

Kwok, Texas A&M University; Afaq Ahmed, Texas A&M University; Andrew Kwok, Texas A&M University

Reimagining Native Teacher Preparation: Early Evaluation Insights from the OIE PD Grant. *Jennifer P Villalobos, Claremont Graduate University; DeLacy E. Ganley, Claremont Graduate University; Victoria Cabrera, Claremont Graduate University; Sonia Baron, Claremont Graduate University*

Teaching is for Girls? Racialized Masculinities, Latino Boys, and Resisting Gender Ideologies. *Omar Davila Jr., Santa Clara University*

Who is Learning Happier: Profiles of Pre-service Teachers' Personality Traits and Relationship with Learning Well-being. *Xingzhou Wang, Beijing Normal University; peili yuan, 北京师范大学, Xinwei Wang; Huan Song, Beijing Normal University*

Chair: *Jolan Smith, California State University - Long Beach*

58.077-8. Terms of Service: Teacher Policy, Contracts, and Governance (Table 8). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Deregulation and Teacher Quality: Educator Preparation Programs React to Removing the EdTPA. *Rachel Garver, Montclair State University; Emily M. Hodge, Virginia Commonwealth University; Drew H. Gitomer, Rutgers University; Colleen McDermott, Rutgers University*

Examining the TEAMS Act's Influence on Rural Secondary Math Teachers: A Mixed Methods Study. *Katina L Stallworth, University of South Alabama; Sohee Kim, University of South Alabama*

Governing Through Mobility: Administrative Rationalities and Urban-Rural Hierarchies in China's Teacher Rotation Policy. *Keyuan Shi, East China Normal University*

Imagining Futures for Teaching Contracts. *uriel abisay martinez sanchez, California State University - San Marcos; Joni Kolman, California State University - San Marcos*

Shifting Discourses in Teacher Education Policy: A Critical Analysis of the Educational Strategies of Türkiye. *Büşra Gündeş Orman, Istanbul Aydin University; Alperen Senol, Istanbul Aydin University*

Chair: *Rachel Garver, Montclair State University*

58.078. AERA Roundtable Session Friday 3:45 pm - Gold 2;
Roundtable Session

58.078-1. Reframing Governance: Policy, Power, and Pathways in Educational Leadership (Table 1). Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Beyond Instrumental Roles: Cultural Brokers in a Chilean RPP. *Bárbara Zoro, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Valparaíso; Manuel A. Pérez-Troncoso, PUCV-CIAE Postdoctoral Researcher; Rebecca Ipinza, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Valparaíso*

Structuring Teacher Recruitment, Development, & Retention Policy to Address Educational Equity Goals. *Kathryn James McGraw, Vanderbilt University; Angela M. Cox, Vanderbilt University*

Teaching Without a License: Historical Lessons and Future Mandates in Texas Education Policy. *Kathryn Dixon, East Texas A&M University; Sarah Guthery, University of Oklahoma; Sara Jolly Jones, Houston Endowment; Carlos Villagrana, Houston Endowment*

Unforgetting the Histories of Hiring: School Board Effects on Superintendent Labor Pathways. *John Matthew Fredericks, Arizona State University*

Chair: *Jeff Walls, University of Iowa*

58.078-2. Imagining Digital Futures: AI, Cell Phones, and Technology Policy in the Digital Age of Schooling (Table 2). Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Caring for the Anxious Generation: Implementing a Cell Phone Ban in a Large Urban District. *Anna Kushner, Teachers College, Columbia University; Jordan Vossen, Independent Researcher; Nathan Johnson, Independent Researcher*

Closing or Widening the Digital Divide? Paradoxical Effects of Digital Education Preparedness on Educational Equity. *Hannah Kim, Seoul National University; Kwangho Jung, Seoul National University; Soojeong Kim, Seoul National University; Sangeon Jin, Seoul National University*

Dialing In or Locking Out? Mapping Texas Districts' Cell Phone Policy Types. *Vinh Pham, University of Houston; Virginia W. Snodgrass Rangel, University of Houston*

Diverging Paths: Critical Policy Analysis of AI Integration in Two Urban Texas School Districts. *April Miles, Texas State University*

Education Governance in the Age of Generative AI: An Exploratory Study of State Policymakers' Perspectives. *Janice Mak, Arizona State University; Carolina Paz Torrejon Capurro, Oklahoma State University; Shagun Singha, Arizona State University*

Chair: *Anna Kushner, Teachers College, Columbia University*

58.078-3. Equity, Inclusion and Intersectionality (Table 3). SIG-Early Education and Child Development; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Understanding Racism, Discrimination, and Prejudice in the Early Learning and Child Care Workforce. *Calpanaa Jegatheeswaran, University of Toronto; Sumayya Saleem, University of Toronto - OISE; Samantha Burns, University of Guelph; Elizabeth Dhuey, University of Toronto - Scarborough; Linda White, University of Toronto; Michal Perlman, University of Toronto - OISE*

Rethinking Equity in Early Childhood Social-Emotional Learning: The Implications of Intersectionality. *Dandan Liang, University of Houston; Xin Li, University of Houston; Tonghui Xu, University of Houston; Jie Zhang, University of Houston*

Possibilities and Challenges of Interactive Family Critical Literacy: A Multiple Case Study with Immigrant Families. *So Jung Kim, University of Hawai'i at Manoa; Shin Ae Han, University of Hawai'i at Manoa*

Reframing Infant-Toddler Behavior in the Persistent Wake of Settler Colonialism. *Carolyn Brennan, Western Washington University; Emmanuelle N. Fincham, Western Washington University*

Chair: *Carolyn Brennan, Western Washington University*

58.078-4. Experiential Education and Community

Engagement: Scholarship and Practice SIG Roundtable 2 (Table 4).

SIG-Experiential Education and Community Engagement: Scholarship and Practice; Roundtable Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

I Am Because We Are: University Students Conceptualize Community through Symbol. *Amy L. Ferrell, University of Colorado - Denver; Lisa Williams, National Center for State Courts; Abigail Rose, University of Colorado - Denver; Mark Simmonds, University of Colorado - Denver*

Institutionalizing Justice: Community Engagement Practices in Higher Education. *Diana Quito, Rollins College; Emily Locke, University of Alabama; Henry Cunningham, University of Louisville; Andrew Pearl, Kansas State University; Tanvi Padalkar, University of Alabama - Birmingham*

Unpacking Wraparound Supports: A Landscape Analysis of Full-Service Community Schools Through a University–Nonprofit Partnership. *Benita R. Brooks, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Omolola Aderonke Odejimi, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Carolina Clavel, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Amy Dawn Wolfe, Clark County School District*

Win-Win-Win Through Community-Engaged Learning from Multiple Stakeholders' Perspectives. *DaeSeok Chai, Texas A&M University; Simon Shin, Texas A&M University; Tania Hasan, Texas A&M University*

Chair: *Elizabeth Dunens, University of Minnesota - Rochester*

58.078-5. Mathematics Beyond the Classroom: Engaging Families and Affecting Communities (Table 5).

SIG-Research in Mathematics Education; Roundtable Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Exploring Affective Engagement in Family Mathematics Through Open-Ended Multi-Touch Design of TouchCounts. *Qiang Lin, Simon Fraser University*

From learning opportunities to being opportunities: Promoting community ontologies in the mathematics classroom. *Salvador Huitzilopochtli, San Jose State University*

From Structure to Justice: Evolving Mathematical Modeling Frameworks Toward Belonging and Civic Transformation. *Eva Thanheiser, Portland State University*

More Math Talk, Less Engagement? The Mediating Role of Negative Feedback in Parent-Child Math Interactions. *Linxi Lu, University of Chicago; Yiling Zhang, Boston College; Nanyu Zhang, Boston College*

Supporting Family Expertise: A Scoping Review of Early Childhood School-Family Math Engagement. *Stephanie C. Calabrese, George Mason University; Leslie La Croix, George Mason University; Jennifer M. Suh, George Mason University; Bweikia Steen, George Mason University*

Chair: *Nicol R. Howard, Chapman University*

58.078-6. Supporting Mathematics Teachers: Leadership and Retention (Table 6).

SIG-Research in Mathematics Education; Roundtable Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Teacher Agency as a Predictor of Retention for Novice Secondary Mathematics Educators. *Christopher Carter, University of Kansas*

Understanding Teacher Retention Among Secondary Mathematics Teachers in Their First Five Years of Teaching. *Babette M. Benken, California State University - Long Beach; Rong-Ji Chen, California State University - San Marcos; Peter Gao, San Jose State University; Sayonita Ghosh Hajra, Sacramento State University; Dennis Kombe, California State University, Monterey Bay; Julie McNamara, California State University East Bay; Ferdinand D. Rivera, San José State University; Cheryl Roddick, San Jose State University; Cristina Runnalls, California State Polytechnic University - Pomona; Agnes Tuska, California State University - Fresno*

The Adaptive Expertise of Mathematics Specialists: Planning to Meet Their Students' Needs. *Melissa A. Gallagher, U.S. Math Recovery Council; Amy Kanagy, US Math Recovery Council*

Evolving Approaches to Mathematics Specialist Research: Reviewing Designs to Guide Future Educational Reform. *Courtney Baker, George Mason University; Katherine*

Edwards, George Mason University; Margret A. Hjalmarsen, National Science Foundation; Kristin E. Harbour, University of South Carolina; Stefanie Livers, Bowling Green State University; Evtthokia Stephanie Saclarides, University of Cincinnati

Artificial Un-intelligence? How Mathematics Coaches Utilize Inaccuracy in an AI Feedback Tool. *Jim Malamut, Stanford University*

Chair: *Tesha Sengupta-Irving, University of California - Berkeley*

58.078-7. Collaborative Approaches for Inclusive Education

(Table 7). SIG-Special and Inclusive Education Research; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Rich Conversations and Data from an Original Board Game on Co-Teaching. *Chris Shamburg, New Jersey City University; Laura Zieger, New Jersey City University; Dana L. Mason, New Jersey City University; Patricia Dennis, Orange Public Schools; Caralee Gately, Washington Township Public Schools; Jacqueline Zamora, Jersey City Board of Education*

Leveraging Friendship Toward Interdisciplinary Collaboration: The Case of One Mathematics Intervention Team. *Erica N. Mason, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Zhuo Chen, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Mercedes Gravley, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Interprofessional teamwork to support inclusive education. *Edda Óskarsdóttir, University of Iceland; Anna Björk Sværisdóttir, University of Iceland*

Preparation and Support for One-to-One Paraprofessionals. *Amanda Agurkis, Long Island University - C.W. Post Campus; Lynn E. Cohen, Long Island University - C.W. Post Campus*

The Relationship between Inclusive Practice, Teacher Backgrounds and School Context. *Xiaoxia A. Newton, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; John William McKenna, University of Massachusetts - Lowell*

Chair: *Erin K. Hogan, University of Louisville*

58.078-8. AI in Preservice Teacher Education: Perceptions, Planning, and Pathways (Table 8).

SIG-Technology as an Agent of Change in Teaching and Learning; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Navigating AI Integration: Early Childhood Pre-Service Teachers' Use of AI Tools in Instructional Planning. *Jaehee Kwon, SUNY at Fredonia*

Cautious Techno-optimism of Generative Artificial Intelligence in Pre-Service Teacher Education. *Mike Karlin, California State University - Dominguez Hills; Cristina Stephany, South*

Bay Consortium Teacher Induction Program; K. 'Alohilani HN Okamura, University of Hawaii 'i at Manoa
Scaffolding AI-Integrated lesson planning: Preservice teachers' use of GenAI through the TPACK framework. *Jaesung Hur, Florida State University; Idam Kim, Florida State University; Nuodi Zhang, Florida State University; Shiyao Wei, Florida State University; Hui Shi, Florida State University; Vanessa Dennen, Florida State University*

The Stress-Adoption Reconfiguration Pathway: Understanding Pre-Service Teachers' Use of GenAI Across a Four-Year Initial Teacher Education Program. *Hsiao-Ping Hsu, Dublin City University; Alan Gorman, Dublin City University*

Chair: *Jialin Yan, University of Rochester*

58.078-9. Capacity and Infrastructure for Responsible AI in Education (Table 9).

SIG-Technology as an Agent of

Change in Teaching and Learning; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;

3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Exploring the Roles of Generative AI in Elementary Education: Collaboration with Teachers in Daily Practice. *Seoyeon Choi, Korea University; Jiyeon Jung, Korea University; Insook Han, Korea University*

From Principles to Practice: Development and Validation of a Teacher GenAI Competency Scale. *Xianhan Huang, The Education University of Hong Kong; Wen SHAO, University of Hong Kong; Shiyu Zhang, The University of Hong Kong*

AI and Educational Leadership: Building Capacity for a Transformative Future. *Nancy Watkins, California State University - Fullerton*

Exploring Key Issues in Learning Data for AI Digital Textbooks. *Young Ri Lee, Ewha Womans University; Seonmin Eun, Seoul National University; Anna Kim, Seoul National University; Young Hoan Cho, Seoul National University*

Chair: *Sanchita Mandal, Tata Institute of Social Sciences - Mumbai*

58.079. AERA Roundtable Session Friday 3:45 pm - Gold 3;

Roundtable Session

58.079-1. Expanding the Development of Faculty (Table 1).

SIG-Faculty Teaching, Evaluation, and Development; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

From Faculty DEI Awareness to Inclusive Teaching: Insights from a Multi-part Survey Study. *Peiwen Wang, Southern Connecticut State University; Amelia Miramonti, University of Nebraska - Lincoln; Sydney E. Brown, University of Nebraska*

Institutional Context Matters: Multilevel Analysis on

Institutional Civic Climate and Faculty Civically Engaged Teaching. *Seonmi Jin, Indiana University; Hee Jung Gong, University of Alabama; Xiaoxia Zhang, Indiana University; Allison BrckaLorenz, Indiana University*

Naming, Reflecting, Becoming: STEM Faculty and the Work of Practice in CoP. *Xinru Yan, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Cherie Avent, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

58.079-2. Critical Examination of Race, Ethnicity, Class, and Gender Roundtable: Experiences of Minoritized Students and Educators in STEM and Male-Dominated Fields (Table 2). SIG-Critical Examination of Race, Ethnicity, Class and Gender in Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

The Ebony Edge: Exploring Math Success Among Black College Women. *April Ruiz, Western Michigan University; Eric Archer, Western Michigan University*

Mapping Persistent Pathways to STEM: A Longitudinal Black Girl Cartography of Philadelphia-based OST-to-College Journeys. *Kimberly Sterin, Drexel University; Janai Keita, Drexel University; Cianni Williams, Drexel University; Ayana Allen-Handy, Hofstra University; Jacqueline Genovesi, Drexel University; Dominique A. Thomas, Drexel University; Kimberly Anne Godfrey, Drexel University; Loni Tabb, Drexel University; Sabrina Afroz, Drexel University*

Nepantla Transgressions: Passageways, Conduits, and Connectors Towards HSI-STEM Transformation. *Carlos A Fitch, University of California - Santa Barbara; M. Magdalena Jimenez Aguilar, University of California - Santa Barbara; Lucy Arellano, University of California - Santa Barbara; Margarita Anahi Rodriguez, University of California - Santa Barbara*

Overcoming Doubt and Finding Belonging: A Phenomenological Exploration of Women's Experiences in Male-Dominated Majors. *Erin Flowers, University of Arkansas at Little Rock; Amanda L. Nolen, Georgia Institute of Technology*

Chair: *Sakeena Everett, University of Connecticut*

58.079-3. Critical Examination of Race, Ethnicity, Class, and Gender Roundtable: Mapping Disparities and Creating "Seats at the Table" for Student Access and Success (Table 3). SIG-Critical Examination of Race, Ethnicity, Class and Gender in Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Postsecondary Outcomes in Gentrifying Areas: A Stratification Economics and QuantCrit Analysis of College Access and

Mobility. *Elizabeth I. Rivera, Montclair State University*
A Seat at The Table: Centering Black Girls' Voices in Access to School-Based Mental Health Support. *Marline Francois-Madden, Morgan State University; Christina Tillery, Virginia Commonwealth University*

Reducing Enrollment Disparities for Prospective Racially Minoritized Graduate Students Through Financial Aid: Evidence from an Online Survey Experiment in the U.S. *Da'Shay P. Templeton, California Lutheran University; Ruslan Korchagin, California Lutheran University*
Exploring Link Between University Housing Policies, Student Belonging, and Discrimination Perceptions for Underrepresented Minority Students. *Jessica Cai, Northwestern University; XunFei Li, University of California - Irvine*

Chair: *Richard A. Orozco, University of Arizona*

58.079-4. Critical Work in Hard Times: Challenging Carcerality in Schools (Table 4). SIG-Grassroots Community and Youth Organizing for Educational Justice; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Friendly Faces, Dangerous Narratives: Examining Copaganda in K-16 Schools. *Noelle Mapes, Graduate Center - CUNY; Jennifer Queenan, Graduate Center - CUNY; Lucien Baskin, Graduate Center - CUNY*

"What Does It Feel Like to Look Up at the Stars?": Curriculum Deliberation Within Confinement. *Rachel McMillian, Indiana University - Indianapolis*

Everyday Resistance: YPAR as a Tool to Counter State Repression in an Ethnic Studies Classroom. *Alo Wilson, California State University - Monterey Bay; Chrissy Hernandez, California State University - Monterey Bay*

The Prison Classroom as a Locus of Abolitionist Struggle. *Ruth Boyajian, Georgia State University*

Jailbreak: Multiracial Resistance, Resilient Praxis, and Community Power Disrupting the School-Prison Nexus. *Guadalupe Ramirez; Steven R. Flores, Chicago Public Schools; Kyndall Jackson, Youth Teams in Education Research; Breanna Lopez, Youth Teams in Education Research; Dulce Gonzalez, Youth Teams in Education Research; Aayla Holiday, Thornton Fractional South*

Continuing the Fight: Deepening Abolitionist World-building & Community Control in NYC Education Justice Movement Organizing. *Imani C. Wilson, New York University; Sohini Das, New York University*

Chair: *Erica R. Meiners, Northeastern Illinois University*

Discussant: *Asif Wilson, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

58.079-5. STEM & Queerness in Education: Disrupting Normativity, Curriculum, and Reimagination (Table 5).

SIG-Queer Studies; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Biology instructor conceptions of acceptability of discussing content about queerness versus other socially controversial topics. *Kris Troy, University of California - Santa Barbara; Royce Olarte, University of California - Santa Barbara; Stanley Lo, University of California - San Diego; Petra Krantzfelder, University of California - Santa Barbara*

Crafting Disruptions to Normativity in a Higher Education STEM Course. *Nickolina Yankova, University of Southern California*

Histories We Carry, Futures We Build: Black Gay Young Men Reimagining Education in the Margins. *Marcus North, Georgia State University; Michelle Zoss, Georgia State University*

Queering Secondary STEM Curriculum. *Kyle C. Nolting, University of Denver*

58.079-6. College Student-Athlete Development, Well-being, Academic and Career Engagement (Table 6). SIG-Research Focus on Education and Sport; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Examining Predictors of Academic and Student Support Engagement Among Community College Athletes. *Agustín J. García, Texas A&M University–Corpus Christi; Carlton J. Fong, Texas State University*

Psychological Fortitude, Well-being, and Sport Satisfaction: A Structural Equation Analysis of College Student-Athletes. *Radomir Ray Mitic, College of William & Mary; Akorede Teriba, University of North Dakota; Jimmy Morin, University of North Dakota*

Reimagining Student-Athlete Engagement: A Restorative and Transformative Justice Approach. *La Quirshia Fennell, Claremont Graduate University*

Total Osprey: A Digital Badge Program for Enhancing College Student-Athlete Career Readiness. *Shujin Zhong, University of North Florida; Jennifer Jackson Kane, University of North Florida; Tara Sunquist, University of North Florida*

58.079-7. Schools as Contexts for Social Emotional Learning (Table 7). SIG-Social and Emotional Learning; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Buffer or barrier: The role of emotional labor in teacher-child relationships and children's social behaviors. *Jing Li, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Barry Bai, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Yang Guo, QingXiu kindergarten; Qin Ji, QingXiu kindergarten; Qiuyun Chen, Jiabaotian*

kindergarten

Building an Emotionally Engaged Classroom: Teacher-Student Emotional Interactions and Their Mechanisms for Practical Strategies. *Huiyi Xu, Zhejiang University*

Challenges and Opportunities in Arizona Schools: Educator Needs Related to Supporting Relationships and Well-being. *Ashley R. McDonald, Arizona State University; Kimberly R. M. Osborne, Arizona State University; Anqi Peng, Arizona State University; Nan Xiao, University of California, Irvine; Brooke Lorraine Johnson, Arizona State University*

Developing a Theory of Change and Evaluation Agenda for Compassionate Systems Leadership. *Suchitra Sarda, University of Illinois at Chicago*

Teacher use of SEL and Student SEL Outcomes: A Comparative Analysis. *Susan Ward Roncalli, Los Angeles Unified School District; Delia Estrada, Los Angeles Unified School District; Marco A. Nava, Los Angeles Unified School District; Jesus Renteria, Los Angeles Unified School District; Octavio Augusto Pescador, Los Angeles Unified School District*

Chair: *Dessy S. Stoycheva, University of Northern Iowa*

58.079-8. Beliefs, Feelings, and (Im)Possibilities (Table 8). SIG-Social Studies Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

A Matter of Belief: Aesthetics and Social Studies Education. *Peter M Nelson, University of British Columbia; Nashwa Moheyyeldine Khedr, University of British Columbia*

Examining Black Students' Emotions and Feelings when Learning Histories of Black Historical Suffering. *Brittany Jones, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

Pedagogical Possibilities: Leveraging the Practices of Social Studies Teachers in Pursuit of New Educational Visions. *Sabrina Leigh Caldwell, University of South Alabama*

Replicating a Vacuum: Gen Z Teachers Experiences of and Teaching for Controversial Issues. *Caiden Webb, University of Missouri; Antonio J. Castro, University of Missouri; Julia Dunn, University of Missouri*

Antisemitism, and Jewish Heritage Knowledge: The Experiences of Jewish Social Studies Teachers at Public Schools. *Emma Eckstein Nicosia, University of Minnesota*

58.079-9. Centering Culture, Identity, and Equity in Mathematics Learning and Teaching (Table 9). Division C - Learning and Instruction; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Braided Brilliance: Ethnomathematics, Identity, and Mathematical Practices in a Black Hair Braiding Camp. *Jessica Showell, Georgia State University; Nickolaus A. Ortiz, Georgia State University*

Designated and Disconnected: Teacher Perspectives on Equity in a 7-12 STEM School. *Courtney Harris, The Ohio State University; Yaa Dankwa, The Ohio State University*

Mapping Mathematical Identities in Motion: Introducing the MINT Framework for Tracing Changes Over Time. *Siqi Huang, University of California - Berkeley*

Justice Through Numbers: Culturally Responsive Math Expeditions for Concept Development and Problem Solving in Upper Elementary Classrooms. *La Toya Caton, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Chair: *Nathan Alexander, Howard University*

58.080. AERA Roundtable Session Friday 3:45 pm - Gold 4;
Roundtable Session

58.080-1. Literacy Development and Achievement across the Lifespan (Table 1). Division C - Learning and Instruction;
Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Designing Accessible Texts for Adults Readers: Comparing Simplified, Authentic, and Parallel Text Versions. *Amanda Jensen, University of Minnesota; Panayiota Kendeou, University of Minnesota*

Does Increased Access to Free Books Improve Reading Achievement? A Randomized Controlled Trial of the Reading Is Fundamental Books for Ownership Program. *Geoffrey D. Borman, Arizona State University; Hyunwoo Yang, The Chinese University of Hong Kong*

Growing Words: An Integrated Framework for Building Vocabulary Knowledge in the Early Grades. *Sen Wang, Boston University; Elizabeth Burke Hadley, University of South Florida - Tampa*

Storytelling Without Words: Fostering Autonomy Through Wordless Picture Books in Emergent Dual-Language Classrooms. *Mariana Gudino Avalos, University of California - Los Angeles; Victoria Arali Daniels, University of California - Los Angeles; Kayeon Koh, University of California - Los Angeles; Christine Lee, University of California - Los Angeles; Arlen Nava, University of California - Los Angeles; Kelly Erin Peters, University of California - Los Angeles*

Third Grade Students' Disciplinary Literacy in Mathematics: Preliminary Findings from Interviews and Eye-Tracking Data. *Sanampreet Gill, Kent State University; Karl W. Kosko, Kent State University; George Kamberelis, Kent State University*

Chair: *Fatima Seyma Kizil, Syracuse University*

58.080-2. Literacy, Identity, and Justice: Critical Perspectives (Table 2). Division C - Learning and Instruction;
Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;

3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Teaching A Raisin in the Sun to Rural, White Students: Missed Opportunities in Perspective Taking. *Matthew L. McConnell, Binghamton University - SUNY; Fantasia Sneed, Binghamton University, State University of New York*

Y is for Yo Mama: Examining First Graders' Pursuit of Joy Through Black Language Play With the Di•VERSE Literacy Curriculum. *Amber Lawson, Bowling Green State University*

More Than Words-Per-Minute: A Hip Hop Approach for Culturally Rooted Fluency Development. *Bianca J. Nightengale-Lee, Western Michigan University; Kandace Lavender, Read Write Kalamazoo; Asif Masum, Western Michigan University*

Chair: *Judith L. Green, University of California - Santa Barbara*

58.080-3. Beyond the Traditional: Critical and Contemporary Examinations of Normalized Narratives, Perspectives, Curriculum, and Practice Across Disciplines (Table 3).

Division C - Learning and Instruction; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Recognizing and Responding to the Problematics of Secondary Social Studies. *Delandrea Hall, University of North Texas; Katy Swalwell; Noreen Naseem Rodriguez, Michigan State University*

Rendering Obedience: Visual Discipline, Subjectivity, and Resistance in Exam-Based Art Education. *Jiayi Guo, University of Georgia*

Making Memory Matter: Constructive Play as Materialized Memory Practice. *Sinyoung Kim, University of Helsinki; Kristiina Kumpulainen, University of British Columbia*

Disrupting Dominant Narratives: Problematizing Pre-Service Teacher Contention with Secondary Sources. *Sydney F. Zentell, Texas A&M University; Sharon D. Matthews, Texas A&M University; Ashlynn Kogut, Texas A&M University; Radhika Viruru, Texas A&M University; Ambyr R. Rios, Kansas State University*

58.080-4. RT5: Advances and Implications for Causal Inference and Power in Randomized Treatment Designs (Table 4).

Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Advancing Causal Inference in Education: Testing Instrument Exogeneity in Pretest-Posttest Designs. *Naram Gwak, Seoul National University*

Power Analysis for Difference-in-Differences Studies with Staggered Treatment Adoption. *Wei Li, University of Florida; Katherine Strickland, University of Florida; Jing Huang, University of Florida; Shuyuan Li, University of*

Florida

Empirical Estimates of Moderator Effects in Cluster Randomized Trials: Implications for Statistical Power and Study Design. *Qi Zhang, American Institutes for Research; Molly E. Cain, American Institutes for Research*

Methodological Updates for Equivalence Tests in Randomized Controlled Trials. *Zuchao Shen, University of Georgia*

Polish the Gold: Calibrating Intervention Effect Estimates for Small-Sample Randomized Controlled Trials. *Yixiao Dong, University of California - Santa Barbara; Garrett J. Roberts, University of Denver*

58.080-5. Method as Presence: Urgency, Belonging, and Relational Praxis in Qualitative Research (Table 5).

Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Metodologias da Urgência: Reclaiming Time, Voice, and Responsibility in Research. *Bruna Damiana Heinsfeld, University of Minnesota*

Shared Sidewalks and Plates: Belonging in Participatory Research. *Amanda Man, University of Delaware; Keondra A Prier, University of Delaware; Soo Bin Jang, University of Delaware*

What Makes Sista Circle Methodology (SCM) Powerful. *Allante Moon, University of Pennsylvania*

58.080-6. Literacy Process and Deaf Protagonism (Table 6).

SIG-Deaf and Hard of Hearing Intersectionalities and Perspectives; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

A Qualitative Analysis of the Strengths and Needs of Deaf Secondary Writers. *Kimberly Wolbers, University of Tennessee; Hannah M. Dostal, University of Connecticut; Kelsey Spurgin, Ball State University; Elizabeth Martinez, University of Tennessee*

Collaborative Shifts: Positioning Educational Interpreters Through Targeted Professional Development. *Lisa M. Prinzi, Rochester Institute of Technology*

Applying Critical Race and Language Theory (LangCrit) in Deaf Education using a Multilingual/Multimodal Approach. *Rezenet Moges, California State University - Long Beach*

Learning from Successful Deaf Adult Readers to Imagine How the Future of Reading Pedagogy May Be Reset. *Marlon H. Kuntze, California School for the Deaf; Hannah M. Dostal, University of Connecticut; Jessica Scott, Georgia State University; Debbie Golos, University of Minnesota; Elaine Gale, Hunter College - CUNY; Stacey Katz Shapiro, American School for the Deaf; Emily Jo Noschese, Wayne State University; Kate Kovacs, California School for the*

Deaf; Julie Sepah, California School for the Deaf

Reclaiming Mathematics Through ASL, Black ASL, and Deaf Ways of Knowing. *Felicia Smith, Minnesota State University - Mankato; Chalandra Gooden, Minnesota State University - Mankato*

Chair: *Ana Luisa Borba Gediell, Federal University of Viçosa*

58.080-7. Learning Processes and Motivation (Table 7). SIG-Motivation in Education Cosponsored with Division C - Learning and Instruction; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

A Meta-analysis of Mobile Learning's Effect on Students' Learning Motivation. *Weichen Wang, East China Normal University; Shuqi Zhou, Donghua University; Zehua Dong, Hangzhou Normal University; Ming Ming Chiu, The Education University of Hong Kong; Wenye Zhou, Institute of Curriculum and Instruction East China Normal University*

Beyond Cognitive Processing: Student Motivational Perceptions and Format Preferences in Concept Mapping. *Deborah G. Fabiyi, Washington State University; Olusola Olalekan Adesope, Washington State University; Vincent OLUWASETO Fakiyesi, University of Georgia; Deborah Moyaki, University of Georgia; Oluwole Fabiyi, Logistic Xpeditors*

From Motivation and Working Memory to Multiple Text Integration: The Mediating Role of Multimodal Reading Engagement. *Zheng Hong Guan, National Yang Ming Chiao Tung University; San Ju Lin, National Yang Ming Chiao Tung University*

Self-Leadership as a Driver of Competency Integration: Evidence from Latent Profile and Network Analyses. *John Jongho Park, Pennsylvania State University; Yewon Kim, Ewha Womans University; Junseo Kim, Korea University; Mihee Park, Auburn University*

Chair: *Martinique Ann Sealy Mitchell, Virginia Commonwealth University*

Division and SIG Posters

58.081. AERA Poster Session Friday 3:45pm; Poster Session

58.081-1. 2026 AERA Undergraduate Fellows Research Poster Fair. AERA Sessions; Invited Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 3:45-5:15pm

Posters:

1. Lived Experiences and the Crisis of (Dis)belief in Education: the Reality at Public Schools in Salvador, Brazil (Poster 1). *Liz Andrade Varela, Davidson College*
2. Why is Youth Civic Engagement So Low? Civics Amnesia

and Other Educational Barriers (Poster 2). *Salma Baksh, Smith College*

3. Everyday Science and Gendered Practices in Latine Families of Young Children (Poster 3). *Catalina Bonanata, New York University*
 4. En sus propias palabras: Understanding the Postsecondary Experiences of Formerly Incarcerated Latinas in California (Poster 4). *Claudia Alexa Castruita, University of California - Los Angeles*
 5. Help or Harm? Exploring the Ethical Impacts of AI in Undergraduate Groupwork (Poster 5). *Sam In Cheang, University of California - Irvine*
 6. An Oral History of the UCLA Prison Education Program: Looking Back to Inform the Future of Prison Education (Poster 6). *Alicia Samantha Ferraez Diaz, University of California - Los Angeles*
 7. Accessibility as a Determinant of STEM Persistence in Early Education (Poster 7). *LaNaiah Frieson, Duke University*
 8. Mapping Educational Inequality: The COVID-19 Impact on St. Louis Public Education (Poster 8). *Cal Marshall Kreuter, Occidental College*
 9. Propelling Youth Towards Anti-Racist Action: The Role of Family and School Ethnic Racial Socialization (Poster 9). *Iris Lazo-Cruz, University of the District of Columbia*
 10. Different Ways of Coping, Different Ways of Learning: How Adaptation Shapes Transferable Skills in Military Conscriptation (Poster 10). *Henry Lee, Northwestern University*
 11. Navigating Early Language Development: The Role of Maternal Education and Cash Assistance in Low-Income Families (Poster 11). *Evelyn (Siyueqi) Li, University of Wisconsin - Madison*
 12. "The Lifeblood of Our Community:" Understanding Historic Black High Schools & Race-Restrictive Education Policy (Poster 12). *Nora Ngo Mitchell, Harvard University*
 13. Evaluating Approaches to Advising Students' Studying Experiences: An Application of (Poster 13). *Madison Peroutka, Vanderbilt University*
 14. Exploring Features of Book Difficulty in Read Alouds with Preschool Children (Poster 14). *Joanna Rydberg, Vanderbilt University*
 15. They Know What They Need: Student Perceptions of "Good Teachers" (Poster 15). *Timothy E. Sims, Vanderbilt University*
 16. Using AI to Combat Math Anxiety (Poster 16). *Helena Tran, University of California - Irvine*
 17. Developmental Language Disorder: Exploring the Diagnostic Accuracy of Parent & Teacher Reports of Bilingual Children's Language Proficiency (Poster 17). *Rachel Aurora Williams, Texas A&M University*
- Chair: *George L. Wimberly, American Educational Research Association*

58.081-2. Making Sense of Complexity in Science Education.

Division C - Learning and Instruction; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 3:45-5:15pm

Posters:

18. Exploring Complex Systems through Venus Flytrap Mechanobiology: High School Students' STEM-integrated Learning with Multiple Models (Poster 18). *Zheng Bian, University of Pennsylvania; Jianan Zhao, University of Pennsylvania; Amanda Cottone, University of Pennsylvania; Susan A. Yoon, University of Pennsylvania*
19. The Social Construction of Geoscience Explanations and the Interplay of Epistemic Risk (Poster 19). *Brandin Conrath, Virginia Commonwealth University; Kathryn M. Bateman, Pennsylvania State University - Harrisburg; Jonathan McCausland, Iona University; Scott McDonald, Pennsylvania State University*
20. Cognitive Patterns of Socio-Scientific Reasoning on a Low-Carbon Campus Among Seventh-Grade Students (Poster 20). *Chengji Luo, Beijing Normal University; Haijian Sun, Beijing Normal University; Jing Lin, Beijing Normal University; Hongyan Zhao, Beijing Normal University*
21. Uncovering College Students' Epistemological Foundations of Interdisciplinary Understanding of Carbon Cycling Through Constructed Responses (Poster 21). *Hyesun You, University of Iowa; Minju Hong, Chung-Ang University*
22. High Tide, Low Coverage: Correlates of Barriers to Teaching About the Ocean In Science Classrooms (Poster 22). *Ella Claire Walsh, Boston College; Laura M. O'Dwyer, Boston College; Victoria Centurino, Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution; Nicholas Bates, Arizona State University - Bermuda Institute of Ocean Sciences; Sonya Dyhrman, Columbia University; Sheean Haley, Columbia University*
23. Misconceptions in the Mojave: Student Understanding Surrounding Complex Ecological Systems (Poster 23). *Nicole J. Thomas, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*
24. Rooted In Place: Using Place-Based Soil Data to Engage Diverse Learners in Data Science (Poster 24). *Ian Thacker, University of Texas - San Antonio; Rebecca Schroeder, University of Texas - San Antonio; Sara Shields-Menard, University of Texas - San Antonio; Mariah Hopkins, University of Texas - San Antonio; Sandrina Ramirez, University of Texas - San Antonio; Corina Lopez, University of Texas - San Antonio; Tanvir Alam, University of Texas - San Antonio*

58.081-3. Educational Equity and the Impact of Structural Bias. Division H - Research, Evaluation and Assessment in Schools; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 3:45-5:15pm

Posters:

25. Attendance STILL matters: The relation between absenteeism and learning in a post pandemic context (Poster

- 25). *Mariana Barragan Torres, University of Illinois System*
26. Predicting Student Performance on a State-Mandated Social Studies Accountability Test (Poster 26). *Kenneth E. Vogler, University of South Carolina; Susan L. Schramm, University of South Carolina*

58.081-4. Trajectories of Transformation: From Preparation to Resistance in Teaching. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 3:45-5:15pm

Posters:

27. “Becoming” Inclusive Educators: Examining Pre-Service to Novice Teacher Learning Trajectories (Poster 27). *Tamara Handy, Teachers College, Columbia University; Maddie Neufeld, Teachers College, Columbia University*
28. Inquiring into Equity: A systematic Review of Equity Research in Professional Learning for K-12 Teachers, 2004-2024 (Poster 28). *Amanda Shear, University of Pennsylvania*
29. “In the darkest times, hope is something you give yourself. That is the meaning of inner strength”: Resistance and Reclamation of Asian American Teachers’ Truths within the Social Studies (Poster 29). *William Hanjin Bae, University of Texas at Austin; Cinthia S. Salinas, University of Texas at Austin*
30. Unlearning Deficit Thinking, Reimagining Inclusion: Preparing Teachers Through the ThinkClusive Framework and Disability Studies in Education (Poster 30). *Hyun Uk Kim, Springfield College*

58.081-5. Constructing Futures of Teacher Education: Equity, Technology, and Transformative Frameworks. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 3:45-5:15pm

Posters:

31. Scaffolding AI Pedagogical Integration: Supporting Early Childhood Teacher Candidates in Culturally Responsive Teaching (Poster 31). *Eun Kyung Ko, National Louis University; Xiaoning Chen, National Louis University; Vishodana Thamotharan, National Louis University; Julie Sidarous, National Louis University*
32. Teaching by Design: Evaluating Cognitive Science Integration in Elementary Educator Preparation (Poster 32). *Cynthia L. Savage, Texas Christian University; Robin R. Griffith, Texas Christian University; Jennifer Smith, Texas Christian University*
33. The Development of Critical Consciousness of Preservice Teachers in a Teacher Preparation Program (Poster 33). *Nadia Alma Saldaña-Spiegle, University of Denver; Maria del Carmen Salazar, University of Denver*
34. Uniting Generic and Content-Specific Instructional Quality to Foster Pre-Service Teachers' Professional Digital

Competence (Poster 34). *Anne-Kathrin Hirsch, University of Rostock; Jo Tondeur, Ghent University; Charlott Rubach, University of Rostock*

35. Using Translanguaging to Shift How Secondary Preservice Teachers Provide Opportunities and Support for Multilingual Learners (Poster 35). *Edward G. Lyon, California State University - Sonoma; Lyn Scott, California State University - East Bay; Caroline Thompson Spurgin, sonoma state university; Saul I. Maldonado, San Diego State University*

58.081-6. CASE Poster Presentations. SIG-Caribbean and African Studies in Education; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 3:45-5:15pm

Poster:

36. Civic Futures in Text: Civic Reasoning and Discourse in African Elementary Education (Poster 36). *Matthew Odebiyi, Arizona State University*

58.081-7. Critical Literacies and Educational Transformation. SIG-Critical Educators for Social Justice; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 3:45-5:15pm

Posters:

37. “It’s Not Going to Stop...so we just gotta go out and play.”: High School Student-Athletes of Color Experiences with Racism and High School Athletics (Poster 37). *George Theoharis, Syracuse University; Christine Elaine Ashby, Syracuse University; Sean Drake, Syracuse University; Lauren Ashby, Syracuse University; ParKer Bryant, Syracuse University*
38. The Impact of Epistemic Oases within Educational Spaces on the Disability Rights Movement (Poster 38). *Rebekah Wallis, Syracuse University; Ethan W Jackson, Syracuse University*
39. The Power of Us: Radical Witnessing and Educator Narratives as Justice Praxis (Poster 39). *Raketa Ouedraogo-Thomas, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Sobeida Velazquez, University of San Diego; Michelle Coleman, Dallas Independent School District; Hannah Mesouani, University of San Diego; Tommy Royston, Anavo Solutions*
40. To Read or Not to Read Challenged Books?: Using Diverse Literature for Literacy Instruction (Poster 40). *Mae Lane, Sam Houston State University; Chyllis Elayne Scott, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Cindy Lee Benge, Eastern New Mexico University; Montana McCormick, Towson University; Ben Morse, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Dana Griffio, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; JoAnn Jones, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*
41. Toward Identifying a Typology of Deficit-Laden Educational Practice: A Systematic Literature Review (Poster 41). *Joonkil Ahn, University of Arizona; Osly J. Flores, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*
42. Towards the democratization of study abroad in the

- American context: Uncovering racism in the application of marketing theory (Poster 42). *Ming Lei, Knox College*
43. A Pig, A Mango, and 15 Minutes: Writing Movidas to Racially Diversify Faculty in Academia (Poster 43). *Norma A. Marrun, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Christine Clark, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*
44. Disrupting Anthropocentric GCE with Ecopedagogies through Southern Epistemological Lenses: Lessons from Bangladesh and Uganda (Poster 44). *Allan Muganga, Beijing Normal University; Jannatul Mawa, Beijing Normal University; Greg William Mistaszek, Tohoku University*

58.081-8. Sketch, Predict, Reflect: Two Prototypes of an Interactive Child-Friendly AI Exhibit. SIG-Informal Learning Environment Research; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 3:45-5:15pm

Poster:

45. Sketch, Predict, Reflect: Two Prototypes of an Interactive Child-Friendly AI Exhibit (Poster 45). *Sihan Cheng, Northwestern University; Lexie Zhao, Northwestern University; John Chen, Northwestern University; Michael S. Horn, Northwestern University*

58.081-9. Social Learning in Affinity Spaces: Analyzing Discussions of Sexual Violence in the RDR 2 Subreddit. SIG-Informal Learning Environment Research; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 3:45-5:15pm

Poster:

46. Social Learning in Affinity Spaces: Analyzing Discussions of Sexual Violence in the RDR 2 Subreddit (Poster 46). *Yue Shi, The University of Hong Kong; Zhongyu Wang, Florida State University; Zhichun Liu, University of Hong Kong*

58.082. e-Lightning Ed-Talk Session 14 - Stage 1. AERA e-Lightning Ed-Talks; AERA Ed Talk
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Exhibit Hall A - Stage 1; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

- “Becoming” Inclusive Educators: Examining Pre-Service to Novice Teacher Learning Trajectories (Stage 1, 3:50 PM). *Tamara Handy, Teachers College, Columbia University; Maddie Neufeld, Teachers College, Columbia University*
- Inquiring into Equity: A systematic Review of Equity Research in Professional Learning for K-12 Teachers, 2004-2024 (Stage 1, 3:59 PM). *Amanda Shear, University of Pennsylvania*
- Unlearning Deficit Thinking, Reimagining Inclusion: Preparing Teachers Through the ThinkClusive Framework and Disability Studies in Education (Stage 1, 4:08 PM). *Hyun Uk Kim, Springfield College*
- Scaffolding AI Pedagogical Integration: Supporting Early

Childhood Teacher Candidates in Culturally Responsive Teaching (Stage 1, 4:17 PM). *Eun Kyung Ko, National Louis University; Xiaoning Chen, National Louis University; Vishodana Thamocharan, National Louis University; Julie Sidarous, National Louis University*

The Development of Critical Consciousness of Preservice Teachers in a Teacher Preparation Program (Stage 1, 4:26 PM). *Nadia Alma Saldaña-Spiegle, University of Denver; Maria del Carmen Salazar, University of Denver*

Uniting Generic and Content-Specific Instructional Quality to Foster Pre-Service Teachers' Professional Digital Competence (Stage 1, 4:35 PM). *Anne-Kathrin Hirsch, University of Rostock; Jo Tondeur, Ghent University; Charlott Rubach, University of Rostock*

Using Translanguaging to Shift How Secondary Preservice Teachers Provide Opportunities and Support for Multilingual Learners (Stage 1, 4:44 PM). *Edward G. Lyon, California State University - Sonoma; Lyn Scott, California State University - East Bay; Caroline Thompson Spurgin, sonoma state university; Saul I. Maldonado, San Diego State University*

Civic Futures in Text: Civic Reasoning and Discourse in African Elementary Education (Stage 1, 4:53 PM). *Matthew Odebiyi, Arizona State University*

Chair: *Judy A. Alston, Miami University (OH)*

58.083. e-Lightning Ed-Talk Session 14 - Stage 2. AERA e-Lightning Ed-Talks; AERA Ed Talk
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Exhibit Hall A - Stage 2; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

- Misconceptions in the Mojave: Student Understanding Surrounding Complex Ecological Systems (Stage 2, 3:50 PM). *Nicole J. Thomas, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*
- Cognitive Patterns of Socio-Scientific Reasoning on a Low-Carbon Campus Among Seventh-Grade Students (Stage 2, 3:59 PM). *Chengji Luo, Beijing Normal University; Haijian Sun, Beijing Normal University; Jing Lin, Beijing Normal University; Hongyan Zhao, Beijing Normal University*
- Exploring Complex Systems through Venus Flytrap Mechanobiology: High School Students' STEM-integrated Learning with Multiple Models (Stage 2, 4:08 PM). *Zheng Bian, University of Pennsylvania; Jianan Zhao, University of Pennsylvania; Amanda Cottone, University of Pennsylvania; Susan A. Yoon, University of Pennsylvania*
- Attendance STILL matters: The relation between absenteeism and learning in a post pandemic context (Stage 2, 4:17 PM). *Mariana Barragan Torres, University of Illinois System*
- Predicting Student Performance on a State-Mandated Social Studies Accountability Test (Stage 2, 4:26 PM). *Kenneth E. Vogler, University of South Carolina; Susan L. Schramm, University of South Carolina*
- “It’s Not Going to Stop...so we just gotta go out and play.”: High School Student-Athletes of Color Experiences with

Racism and High School Athletics (Stage 2, 4:35 PM).
George Theoharis, Syracuse University; Christine Elaine Ashby, Syracuse University; Sean Drake, Syracuse University; Lauren Ashby, Syracuse University; ParKer Bryant, Syracuse University

The Impact of Epistemic Oases within Educational Spaces on the Disability Rights Movement (Stage 2, 4:44 PM).
Rebekah Wallis, Syracuse University; Ethan W Jackson, Syracuse University

The Power of Us: Radical Witnessing and Educator Narratives as Justice Praxis (Stage 2, 4:53 PM). *Raketa Ouedraogo-Thomas, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Sobeida Velazquez, University of San Diego; Michelle Coleman, Dallas Independent School District; Hannah Mesouani, University of San Diego; Tommy Royston, Anavo Solutions*

To Read or Not to Read Challenged Books?: Using Diverse Literature for Literacy Instruction (Stage 2, 5:02 PM). *Mae Lane, Sam Houston State University; Chyllis Elayne Scott, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Cindy Lee Benge, Eastern New Mexico University; Montana McCormick, Towson University; Ben Morse, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Dana Griffo, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; JoAnn Jones, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*

Chair: *Rebecca A. Maynard, University of Pennsylvania*

Friday, April 10th, 5:45 pm

AERA Sessions

59.010. 2026 AERA Presidential Address - The Future Is Here: Historical Signals in Education Research. AERA Sessions; Invited Speaker Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Concourse Hall; 5:45-7:15pm

Speaker: *Maisha T. Winn, Stanford University*

Friday, April 10th, 7:00 pm

60.010. University of Vermont - College of Education and Social Services Dean's Reception. Affiliated Groups; Reception
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 6th Floor, Metropolitan; 7:00-8:30pm

Friday, April 10th, 7:15 pm

61.010. Chinese University of Hong Kong Education Reception. Affiliated Groups; Reception
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor,

Wilshire Grand Ballroom I; 7:15-9:15pm

61.011. Colorado Reception. Affiliated Groups; Reception
Westin Bonaventure, Level 3, Emerald Bay; 7:15-9:15pm

61.012. Texas Tech University College of Education Reception. Affiliated Groups; Reception
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 6th Floor, Executive Boardroom I and Foyer; 7:15-9:15pm

61.013. University of Iowa College of Education's Annual Alumni and Friends Reception. Affiliated Groups; Reception
Westin Bonaventure, Level 3, Hollywood Ballroom; 7:15-9:00pm

Friday, April 10th, 7:30 pm

62.010. The University of Alabama College of Education Reception. Affiliated Groups; Reception
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Atrium III; 7:30-9:30pm

62.011. University of Missouri College of Education & Human Development Reception. Affiliated Groups; Reception
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 409AB; 7:30-9:30pm

Friday, April 10th, 7:45 pm

AERA Related Activities

63.010. AERA Publications Closed Reception. AERA Related Activities; Reception
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 406AB; 7:45-9:15pm
Chair: *John Neikirk, American Educational Research Association*

Division Sessions

63.011. Division B and C Joint Reception. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Reception
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum E; 7:45-9:15pm
Chairs: *Helenrose Fives, Montclair State University; Theodora Regina Berry, Bloomfield College of Montclair State University*

63.012. Division F Business Meeting and Reception. Division F
- Historical Inquiry in Education; Business Meeting
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 402A;
7:45-9:45pm

Chair: *Jon Hale, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

SIG Sessions

63.013. Abolition and Carceral Studies in Education SIG Business Meeting. SIG-Abolition and Carceral Studies in Education; Business Meeting
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 303A;
7:45-8:45pm

Chair: *Julissa O. Muñiz, University of California - Los Angeles*

Participants: *Uriel Serrano, University of Southern California; Cydney Y. Caradonna, University of Utah; Nalya Arabelle Fenella Rodriguez, California State University - Northridge; David O. Stovall, University of Illinois at Chicago; Miguel Cesar, University of Alabama; Armando Lizarraga, University of Texas at Austin*

63.014. Advanced Study of National Databases (ASOND) Business Meeting. SIG-Advanced Studies of National Databases; Business Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Level 3, Avalon; 7:45-8:45pm

63.015. Arts & Inquiry SIG Business Meeting. SIG-Arts and Inquiry in the Visual and Performing Arts in Education; Business Meeting
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 301A;
7:45-8:45pm

Chair: *Daniel X. Harris, RMIT University*

Officers: *Andrea E. Allen, Michigan State University; Mary Beth Cancienne, James Madison University; Carolina Bergonzoni, Cape Breton University*

63.016. Bilingual Education Research SIG - Business Meeting. SIG-Bilingual Education Research; Business Meeting
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 403B;
7:45-8:45pm

Chair: *Cristian R. Aquino-Sterling, Texas Tech University*

Officers: *Suzanne Garcia, California State University - Monterey Bay; Zhongfeng Tian, Rutgers University - Newark; Rouhollah Aghasaleh, California State Polytechnic University - Humboldt; Minhye Son, California State University - Dominguez Hills; Cori Salmerón, Georgia State University; Susana Ibarra Johnson, New Mexico State University*

63.017. Brain, Neurosciences and Education SIG Business meeting. SIG-Brain, Neurosciences and Education; Business Meeting

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum H; 7:45-8:45pm

Chairs: *Kay Brocato, Mississippi State University; Yu Zhang, Tsinghua University*

Officers: *Naomi Malone, Cybermedia Technologies; Tracey N. Tokuhama-Espinosa, Harvard University Extension School; Sameera Massey, Texas A&M University - Corpus Christi; Feliza Marie Mercado, Texas Tech University; Luciano Cid, Biola University; Kent A. Divoll, University of Houston - Clear Lake; Kristin Simmers, University of Connecticut*

63.018. SIG Computer and Internet Applications in Education Business Meeting. SIG-Computer and Internet Application in Education; Business Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Los Cerritos; 7:45-8:45pm

Chair: *Chin-Hsi Lin, University of Hong Kong*

Participants: *Kyungbin Kwon, Indiana University; Olha Ketsman, Northern Illinois University; Yan Chen, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Kendall Hartley, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*

63.019. Constructing the Future with Smart Innovation: Constructivist Theory, Research, and Practice SIG Business Meeting. SIG-Constructivist Theory, Research, and Practice; Business Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Beaudry A; 7:45-8:45pm
Participant: *LaTeshia Warren, Mercer University*

63.020. Deaf and Hard of Hearing Intersectionalities and Perspectives SIG Business Meeting. SIG-Deaf and Hard of Hearing Intersectionalities and Perspectives; Business Meeting
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 301B;
7:45-8:45pm
Chair: *Hannah M. Dostal, University of Connecticut*
Officers: *Colleen L. Smith, California State University - Northridge; Ana Luisa Borba Gediell, Federal University of Viçosa; Gabrielle A. Jones, University of California - San Diego*

63.021. Decolonial, Postcolonial, and Anti-Colonial Studies in Education. SIG-Decolonial, Postcolonial, and Anti-Colonial Studies in Education; Business Meeting
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 403A;
7:45-8:45pm
Chair: *Jairo I. Fúnez-Flores, Independent Researcher*
Moderator: *Alexandra Allweiss, Michigan State University*

63.022. Design and Technology SIG Business Meeting. SIG-Design and Technology; Business Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Santa Barbara C; 7:45-8:45pm

Chair: *Yvonne Earnshaw, Kennesaw State University*
Officer: *Sangeetha Carmona, California State University - Fullerton*

63.023. Early Education Child Development SIG Business Meeting and Reception. SIG-Early Education and Child Development; Business Meeting
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 7; 7:45-9:15pm

Chair: *Jennifer Jo Baumgartner, Louisiana State University*

63.024. Educational Statisticians SIG Business Meeting. SIG-Educational Statisticians; Business Meeting
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 6th Floor, Palace; 7:45-8:45pm

Chair: *Xinya Liang, University of Arkansas*

Speaker: *Craig K. Enders, University of California - Los Angeles*

63.025. Y-PARchiving and Localized Histories Youth-Led Workshop and GCYO Business Meeting. SIG-Grassroots Community and Youth Organizing for Educational Justice; Business Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, San Gabriel A; 7:45-8:45pm

Chair: *Ana Carolina Fernandes de Bessa Antunes, University of Utah*

Co-Chairs: *Shreya Sunderram, Graduate Center - CUNY; Julissa Ventura, Marquette University; Naomi Mae W., University of Wisconsin - Madison; Karen Zaino, Miami University (OH); Daicy Diaz-Granados, Center for Puerto Rican Studies*

63.026. Holistic Education SIG Business Meeting. SIG-Holistic Education; Business Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, La Cienega; 7:45-8:45pm

Chair: *Deepa Srikantaiah, American University*

Officers: *Steven Haberman, University of Central Florida; Michelle L. Tichy, Alfred University*

63.027. Immigration and Education SIG Business Meeting. SIG-Immigration and Education; Business Meeting
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304C; 7:45-8:45pm

Chairs: *Rabia Hos, Southern Connecticut State University; Chandler Patton Miranda, Molloy University*

Participants: *Adnan Turan, Arizona State University; Alicia Rusoja, University of California - Davis; Edom Tesfa, Brown University; Sophia L. Angeles, Pennsylvania State University; Elizabeth Davis, George Mason University; Fiza Mairaj, University of Houston; Brian Tauzel, Western Washington University*

63.028. Inclusion and Accessibility in Educational Assessment Business Meeting and Reception (SIG 96). SIG-Inclusion and Accessibility in Educational Assessment; Business Meeting
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 7th Floor, Hollywood Ballroom I; 7:45-8:45pm

Chair: *Shelbi Cole, Student Achievement Partners*

Discussant: *Mary Cochoran, Metimur*

63.029. Indigenous Peoples of the Americas Business Meeting. SIG-Indigenous Peoples of the Americas; Business Meeting
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 6; 7:45-8:45pm

Chair: *Kelly Leah Stewart, University of California, Los Angeles*

Co-Chair: *Theresa J. Stewart-Ambo, University of California - Los Angeles*

63.030. Innovative School Transformation and Reform (ISTaR) SIG Business Meeting. SIG-Innovative School Transformation and Reform; Business Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Palos Verdes; 7:45-8:45pm

Chair: *Kathleen Provinzano, Binghamton University - SUNY*

Co-Chair: *Kerstin A. Carlson Le Floch, American Institutes for Research*

Officer: *Erica Harbatkin, Florida State University*

63.031. Latina/o/x Research Issues SIG Business Meeting. SIG-Latina/o/x Research Issues; Business Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Level 3, Santa Monica B; 7:45-8:45pm

Chair: *Rachel F. Gomez, Virginia Commonwealth University*

Officers: *Cynthia D. Villarreal, Northern Arizona University; José Reyes Del Real Viramontes, University of California - Riverside*

63.032. Learning Environments SIG Business Meeting. SIG-Learning Environments; Business Meeting
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 9; 7:45-8:45pm

Chair: *Paul E. Rijken, University of Adelaide*

Officer: *Ridwan Maulana, University of Groningen*

63.033. Advanced Technologies for Learning SIG & Learning Sciences SIG Joint Business Meeting and Reception. SIG-Learning Sciences; Business Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Beaudry B; 7:45-8:45pm

Chairs: *Kathryn Lanouette, William & Mary; Tingting Li, Washington State University*

63.034. Business Meeting: Lesson Study SIG. SIG-Lesson Study; Business Meeting
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum F; 7:45-8:45pm

Chair: *Gloriana Gonzalez, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

63.035. Lives of Teachers SIG Business Meeting. SIG-Lives of Teachers; Business Meeting
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum G; 7:45-8:45pm

Chair: *Lora Bartlett, University of California - Santa Cruz*
Officers: *Alisun Thompson, University of Puget Sound; Amber Pabon, Kutztown University of Pennsylvania; Rebecca Buchanan, University of Maine; Tim Pressley, Christopher Newport University*

63.036. SIG 64 Measurement and Assessment in Higher Education Business Meeting. SIG-Measurement and Assessment in Higher Education; Business Meeting
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 6th Floor, Broadway; 7:45-8:45pm

Chair: *Elizabeth E. Smith, Eastern Kentucky University*
Co-Chairs: *Lisette Tolentino, University of Florida; Xiaomei Song, Case Western Reserve University*

63.037. Imagining Just Educational Futures Through Media and Literacies Partnerships in Precarious Times (Same as Writing and Literacies SIG). SIG-Media, Culture, and Learning Cosponsored with SIG-Writing and Literacies; Business Meeting
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 10; 7:45-8:45pm

Chair: *T. Philip Nichols, Baylor University*
Officers: *Grace D. Player, University of Connecticut; Stephanie Rollag Yoon, Minnesota State University - Mankato; Karis Michelle Jones, Baylor University; Victoria Gill, Lesley University; Veena Vasudevan, University of Pittsburgh; T. Philip Nichols, Baylor University*
Panelists: *Tracey Terece Flores, University of Texas at Austin; Kareem Edouard, Drexel University; Tiera C. Tanksley, University of Colorado - Boulder; Edward R. Curammeng, California State University - Dominguez Hills*

63.038. Multicultural/Multiethnic Education: Theory, Research, and Practice Business Meeting. SIG-Multicultural/Multiethnic Education: Theory, Research and Practice; Business Meeting
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 1; 7:45-8:45pm

Chair: *Christopher J.P. Sewell, Colorado College*
Participants: *Allen Christopher Williams, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Neisha Terry Young, Stony Brook University - SUNY; Melisa M. Valentin, Western Governors University; Paul G. Sauberer, University of South Florida; Maria Zaman, University of North Dakota; Cameron Scott White, Alabama A&M University; Crystal Hutchinson, Rowan University*

63.039. Multiple Linear Regression: General Linear Model SIG Business Meeting. SIG-Multiple Linear Regression: The General Linear Model; Business Meeting
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Los Feliz; 7:45-8:45pm

Chair: *Jingshun Zhang, Florida Gulf Coast University*
Officers: *Yanli Xie, Florida State University; Xiao Liu, University of Texas at Austin*

63.040. Music Education SIG Business Meeting. SIG-Music Education; Business Meeting
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Georgia I; 7:45-8:45pm

Chair: *Olivia Tucker, University of Utah*

63.041. NAEP Studies SIG Business Meeting. SIG-NAEP Studies; Business Meeting
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 6th Floor, Century; 7:45-8:45pm

Chair: *B. Jasmine Park, American Institutes for Research*
Officer: *Judy H. Tang, Westat*

63.042. Out-of-School Time SIG Business Meeting. SIG-Out-of-School Time; Business Meeting
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 501B; 7:45-8:45pm

Chair: *Sabrina J. Curtis, University of Virginia*
Officers: *Charmaine Davis-Grant, Department of Education and Workforce (DEW); Ishmael Miller, Arizona State University*

63.043. Politics of Education SIG Business Meeting. SIG-Politics of Education; Business Meeting
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 8; 7:45-8:45pm

Chair: *Cory T. Brown, The Ohio State University - Newark*
Participants: *Rachel Sue White, University of Texas at Austin; Travis E. Dumas, Rutgers University; Rachel E. Williams, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Diana D'Amico Pawlewicz, University of North Dakota*
Moderator: *DeMarcus A Jenkins, University of Pennsylvania*

63.044. To Go Back and Retrieve: Fugitive Histories and Black Educational Futures — RFBE SIG 2025 Business Meeting. SIG-Research Focus on Black Education; Business Meeting
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 408A; 7:45-8:45pm

Chair: *Lakia M Scott, Yale University*

63.045. Distinguished Scholar Address with Dr. Elfrieda (Freddy) H. Hiebert and Dr. Sarah M. Lupo at Research

in Research & Literacy SIG 11 Business Meeting. SIG-Research in Reading and Literacy; Business Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Level 2, Beverly; 7:45-8:45pm

Chair: *Emily M. Rodgers, The Ohio State University*

Speakers: *Elfrieda H. Hiebert, TextProject; Sarah M. Lupo, James Madison University*

Officers: *John Z. Strong, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Tracy Johnson, University of Indianapolis; Jeanne Sinclair, Memorial University of Newfoundland; Patrick Burke, Dublin City University*

63.046. Research on Giftedness, Creativity, and Talent SIG Business Meeting. SIG-Research on Giftedness, Creativity and Talent; Business Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Level 2, Mt. Washington; 7:45-8:45pm

Chair: *Jennifer L. Jolly, University of Alabama*

63.047. Research on Women in Education (RWE) SIG Business Meeting. SIG-Research on Women and Education; Business Meeting
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304B; 7:45-8:45pm

Chair: *Vanessa E. Vega, University of Central Florida*

Officers: *Pamela L. Gray, New Mexico State University; Chadrhyn A.A. Pedraza, New Mexico State University; LeAnne C. Salazar Montoya, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*

63.048. Research Use SIG Business Meeting. SIG-Research Use; Business Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, La Brea; 7:45-8:45pm

Chair: *Jenna Doane, The University of New Mexico*

63.049. School Effectiveness and School Improvement SIG Business Meeting. SIG-School Effectiveness and School Improvement; Business Meeting
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Georgia II; 7:45-8:45pm

Chair: *Jennifer Watters, University of Texas - Tyler*

63.050. Semiotics in Education: Signs, Meanings and Multimodality Business Meeting. SIG-Semiotics in Education: Signs, Meanings and Multimodality; Business Meeting
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 501C; 7:45-8:45pm

Chairs: *Angel Mei Yi Lin, The Education University of Hong Kong; Sabrina F. Sembiane, Florida Atlantic University; Katarina N. Silvestri, SUNY - College at Cortland*

63.051. Systems Thinking in Education SIG Business Meeting. SIG-Systems Thinking in Education; Business Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, San Gabriel B; 7:45-8:45pm

Chair: *Linda K. Mayger, The College of New Jersey*
Co-Chair: *Lok-Sze Wong, University of North Texas*
Officers: *Sharon I. Radd, St. Catherine University; Whitney M. Hegseth, University of La Verne*

63.052. Teaching and Learning Research Methods (TLRM) SIG Business Meeting and Invited Speakers. SIG-Teaching and Learning Research Methods; Business Meeting
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Echo Park; 7:45-8:45pm

Chair: *Jennifer Richardson McGee, Appalachian State University*
Co-Chairs: *Vicki L. Plano Clark, University of Cincinnati; Megan K. Mitchell, University of Central Florida*
Speakers: *Anastasia Kitsantas, George Mason University; Timothy J. Cleary, Rutgers University*

63.053. SIG 147 Urban Learning Teaching and Research Business Meeting: Whats Next for Urban Education. SIG-Urban Learning, Teaching, and Research; Business Meeting
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 2; 7:45-8:45pm

Chair: *Katrina Liu, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*

Friday, April 10th, 8:00 pm

64.010. Michigan State University College of Education Reception. Affiliated Groups; Reception
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Wilshire Grand Ballroom II; 8:00-11:00pm

64.011. Montclair State University College for Education and Engaged Learning Reception. Affiliated Groups; Reception
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, San Fernando; 8:00-10:00pm

64.012. University of Maryland Alumni & Friends Reception. Affiliated Groups; Reception
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 5; 8:00-10:00pm

Friday, April 10th, 8:15 pm

Division Sessions

65.010. Division B Business Meeting. Division B - Curriculum Studies; Business Meeting

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum A; 8:15-9:15pm

Chair: *Theodora Regina Berry, Bloomfield College of Montclair State University*

Participants: *Jacque Forbes, Dickinson College; Dowan A. McNair-Lee, University of the District of Columbia*

65.011. Division C Business Meeting. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Business Meeting
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum B; 8:15-9:15pm

Chairs: *DeLeon Gray, North Carolina State University; Emily Quinn Rosenzweig, Teachers College, Columbia University*
Officer: *Helenrose Fives, Montclair State University*

Friday, April 10th, 8:45 pm

SIG Sessions

66.010. Joint Arts Party. SIG-Arts and Inquiry in the Visual and Performing Arts in Education Cosponsored with SIG-Arts and Learning and SIG-Arts-Based Educational Research, SIG-Elliot Eisner; Reception
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 303A; 8:45-10:15pm

Chairs: *Daniel X. Harris, RMIT University; Mary Beth Cancienne, James Madison University; Carolina Bergonzoni, Cape Breton University; Andrea E. Allen, Michigan State University; Courtney Mauldin-Jones, Syracuse University; Matt Omasta, Miami University (OH); Jennifer Bartee, University of the District of Columbia*

66.011. RFBE Reception: Hussle and Flow. SIG-Research Focus on Black Education Cosponsored with SIG-Critical Educators for Social Justice; Reception
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 408B; 8:45-10:15pm

Chair: *Khalilah Odessa Ali, Spelman College*

Saturday, April 11th, 7:00 am

AERA Related Activities

67.010. AERA Undergraduate Student Workshop - Day 4 (Invitation Only). AERA Related Activities; Workshop
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 505; 7:00-10:00am

Chair: *George L. Wimberly, American Educational Research Association*

AERA Sessions

67.011. Combined Social Justice Awards Breakfast. AERA Sessions; Reception
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 403A; 7:00-8:00am

Chair: *George L. Wimberly, American Educational Research Association*

Committee Sessions

67.012. AERA Graduate Student Resource Center (Day 4). Graduate Student Council; Networking Center
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 502B; 7:00am to 6:45pm

67.013. National Academy of Education Members Breakfast. Affiliated Groups; Seminar
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Wilshire Grand Ballroom I; 7:00-10:00am

Saturday, April 11th, 7:30 am

Division Sessions

68.010. Division I Teaching and Learning Community Meeting (Closed Meeting). Division I - Education in the Professions; Board Meeting
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 408A; 7:30-8:30am

Chairs: *Toni Ungaretti, Johns Hopkins University; Peggy Gesing, Old Dominion University*

Participants: *Violet Kulo, University of Maryland - Baltimore; Yuane Jia, Rutgers University*

Saturday, April 11th, 7:45 am

Professional Development Courses

69.010. PD26-15 An Introduction to Missing Data Analyses for Educational Research. Professional Development and Training Committee; Professional Development Course
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Plaza I; 7:45-11:45am

69.011. PD26-16 Crafting Autoethnography: From Personal Experience to Scholarly Insight. Professional Development and Training Committee; Professional Development Course
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Plaza II;
7:45-11:45am

AERA Sessions

69.012. The Revision of the Testing Standards: Operations (Invited Joint AERA/NCME Session). AERA Sessions
Cosponsored with NCME; Invited Speaker Session
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor,
Wilshire Grand Ballroom III; 7:45-9:15am
Chair: *Yeran Tong, University of Pennsylvania*
Presenters: *Ye Tong, National Board of Medical Examiners; Qiwei He, Georgetown University; Rochelle S. Michel, Smarter Balanced Assessment Consortium; Cara Cahalan Laitusis, Center for Assessment; Stephen E. Stark, University of South Florida; Andres De Los Reyes, University of Maryland; Michael C. Rodriguez, University of Minnesota*
Discussant: *Andres De Los Reyes, University of Maryland*

Committee Sessions

69.013. Navigating Power and Conflict: Fostering Growth Through Difficult Conversations in Graduate School. Graduate Student Council; Invited Speaker Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 402A;
7:45-9:15am
Chair: *Cammie Justus-Smith, Virginia Commonwealth University*
Panelists: *Kamaria B. Porter, Northwestern University; Shannon Lynn Burton, Michigan State University*

69.014. Re-imagining Equitable Inclusion: Immigrant and Refugee Parents and Youths' Experiences of Disengagement. Committee on Scholars of Color in Education; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 501B;
7:45-9:15am
Participants:
Immigrant and Refugee Parents and Youth's Enactments of Solidarities for Social Change. *Mariana Pacheco, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Taucia Gonzalez, University of Arizona; Hetal Ascher Patel, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Andrea Espinoza, University of Arizona; Carlos Orozco-Wagner, University of Wisconsin-Madison*
"The child is mine and he is yours too": Hmong Parents' Care as Educational Advocacy. *Hetal Ascher Patel, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Mariana Pacheco, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Taucia Gonzalez, University of Arizona; Andrea Espinoza, University of Arizona; Carlos Orozco-Wagner, University of Wisconsin-Madison*

Learning from the Margins: Spacemaking and Radical Belonging among Bi/Multilingual Youth. *Carlos Orozco-Wagner, University of Wisconsin-Madison; Mariana Pacheco, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Taucia Gonzalez, University of Arizona; Hetal Ascher Patel, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Andrea Espinoza, University of Arizona*

Agents/Angels of Disruption: Bi/Multilingual Latine Parents Navigating and Resisting Special Education Systems. *Andrea Espinoza, University of Arizona; Taucia Gonzalez, University of Arizona; Mariana Pacheco, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Carlos Orozco-Wagner, University of Wisconsin-Madison; Hetal Ascher Patel, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Chair: *Joan J. Hong, University of Maryland*
Discussant: *Linn E. Posey-Maddox, Temple University*

Division Sessions

69.015. Constructing New Visions of Educational Leadership through Political Literacy. Division A - Administration; Symposium
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Los Cerritos; 7:45-9:15am
Participants:
Creative Maladjustment: Navigating Regressive Times through Political Literacy in Educational Leadership. *Tina Mitchell, Delaware State University; Chetanath Gautam, Delaware State University*
Empowering Educational Leaders as Equity Advocates: Strategies for Navigating Policy through IDEAL. *Robert White, ECSU*
Principal Success and Political Contexts: A Meta-Synthesis of Two Decades of International Cases. *Junqi Lin, University of Alabama; Jingping Sun, University of Alabama; Bob L. Johnson, University of Alabama*
Leadership Strategies and Protocols to Develop Stakeholder Political Literacy. *Dayna Lynn Mitchell, California State Polytechnic University - Pomona*
Developing School Leadership to Address Nationalism and Politicization in U.S. and Europe. *Tom Shields, University of Richmond; Pierre Tulowitzki, FHNW University of Applied Sciences and Arts Northwestern Switzerland*
AI Technologies and Political Literacy in K-12 Democratic Schooling. *Koksai Banoglu, The Education University of Hong Kong*
Chair: *Charles L. Lowery, Virginia Tech*
Discussant: *Charles L. Lowery, Virginia Tech*

69.016. Interpreting, Negotiating, Teaching: The Role of Teachers in Producing and Disrupting Curriculum. Division B - Curriculum Studies; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304B;

7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Becoming Context-Strategic: Navigating the Tensions of Social Justice Curriculum Design within Teachers' School Context. *Kierstin M. Giunco, University of Cincinnati; Katherine L. McNeill, Boston College*

Curriculum as Situated Practice: A Case Study of Early Childhood Teachers' Interpretive Work. *Sinan Yozgatli, Indiana University*

Teaching Against the Tide: Justice-Oriented Educators Confront Fascist Currents in U.S. Schools. *Kushya Sugarman, Mount Holyoke College; Laura A Taylor, Rhodes College*

The Impact of Teachers on Students' Narratives of United States History. *Erica J Nelson, University of Iowa*

Chair: *Sarah A Caroleo, Brown University*

69.017. Advancing Mathematics Teaching and Learning Through Targeted Professional Learning and Digital Supports. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Paper Session

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Beaudry B; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Meeting Teachers Where They Are: A Mixed-Methods RCT of Early Childhood Mathematics Professional Development.

Douglas H. Clements, University of Denver; Julie Sarama, University of Denver; Douglas Ready, Teachers College, Columbia University; Samantha Parang, Teachers College, Columbia University; Rebecca Shmoys, Teachers College, Columbia University; Crystal A Day-Hess, University of Denver; Christina D. Mulcahy, University of Denver; Kayleigh Hoagland, Teachers College, Columbia University

Rural Impact: An Online Math Platform Augmented with Virtual Professional Learning. *Mingyu Feng, WestEd; Linlin Li, WestEd; Megan Schneider, WestEd*

Teachers Exploring Proportional Reasoning through Digital Representations: Reasoning with Invariance vs. Showing the Answer. *Gal Gili Nagar, University of Massachusetts - Dartmouth; Chandra H. Orrill, Rethink Learning Labs; Rachael Eriksen Brown, Pennsylvania State University - Abington; Kun Wang, Rethink Learning Labs*

Using Students' Mathematical Writing as a tool for Teacher Professional Development. *Amanda Reinsburrow, Drexel University; Valerie Klein, Drexel University; Wesley Shumar, Drexel University*

69.018. AI and Immersive Technologies in Language Learning and Communication. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Paper Session

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Los Feliz; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Comparing the Impact of Synchronous and Asynchronous Generative AI -Assisted Learning in Language Education. *Zhihui Zhang, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Thomas*

K.F. Chiu, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Scott Aubrey, The Chinese University of Hong Kong

From Attributes to Action: How Global Learners Utilize ChatGPT in Self-Directed Learning. *Belle Li, Purdue University; Victoria Lynn Lowell, Purdue University*

Imagining Futures Through Student-Centered AI-Informal Digital Learning of English Practices in a Resource-limited EFL Context. *Wan Yee Winsy Lai, The Education University of Hong Kong; Ju Seong Lee, The Education University of Hong Kong*

Seeing from the Stage: How Virtual Reality Shapes Rhetorical Understanding through Embodied Learning. *Meryem Yilmaz Soyly, Georgia Institute of Technology; Kelly Williams, Georgia Institute of Technology; Alison E Valk, Georgia Institute of Technology; Jeonghyun Lee, Georgia Institute of Technology*

Chair: *Suriati Abas, SUNY Oneonta*

69.019. Unpacking Self-Regulated Learning: Cognitive, Motivational, and Methodological Insights Across Developmental and Disciplinary Contexts. Division C - Learning and Instruction Cosponsored with SIG-Studying and Self-Regulated Learning; Paper Session

Westin Bonaventure, Level 3, Avalon; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Do Metacognitive-Supportive Exit Tickets in Middle School Math Classrooms Improve Students' Self-regulated Learning? *Xinran Wang, Vanderbilt University; Jerry Nelluvelil, Harvard University; Madeleine Kingan, Harvard University; Rebecca Adler, Vanderbilt University; Lingfei Cao, Vanderbilt University; Cristina D. Zepeda, Vanderbilt University; Jon R. Star, Harvard University; Bethany Rittle-Johnson, Vanderbilt University; Kelley Durkin, Vanderbilt University*

Epistemic Network Analysis and Multigroup Modeling Reveals Domain Specific Self-Regulated and Active Learning in Biology. *Hanall Sung, University of Tennessee; Jeff A. Greene, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Matthew L. Bernacki, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Michael Abdul Ghani Berro, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Linyu Yu, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Robert D Plumley, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*

Exploring self-reported achievement goal orientation as a predictor of keystroke logging behavior patterns interpreted via a lens of self-regulated learning. *Sierra Outerbridge, University of Central Florida; Michelle Taub, University of Central Florida; Joel Schneier, University of Central Florida; LaVonda R. Walker, University of Central Florida*

Factors Influencing Cognitive Load: Exploring Affective Elements, Motivational Constructs, and Regulatory Strategies in Learning. *Rebecca B. Brockbank, Utah State University; David F. Feldon, Utah State University; Kaylee Litson, University of Houston*

Individual Differences in Early Self-Regulatory Mechanisms: Bayesian Regularized Latent Class Analysis of Preschoolers' Learning Trajectories. *YUNQI WANG, The Education University of Hong Kong; Chengrui Wang, Fudan University; DA GONG, The Education University of Hong Kong*

Chair: *Madeleine Kingan, Harvard University*

Discussant: *Jeff A. Greene, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*

69.020. Innovations in Validity Evaluation and Measurement Development. Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Paper Session
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 7th Floor, Hollywood Ballroom I; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

An R Shiny App for Calculating Consequential Validity Ratio with Continuous and Binary Criterion. *Kushmakar Baral, University of Denver; Yixiao Dong, University of California - Santa Barbara*

Beyond Alignment Claims: Analyzing Content Validity Evidence in K-8 Mathematics State Testing Programs. *Eunjung Myoung, Stanford University; Maria Araceli Ruiz-Primo, Stanford University*

Evaluating the Classification Accuracy of an Automated Writing Evaluation System as a Universal Writing Screener in Middle School. *Fan Zhang, University of Delaware; Joshua Wilson, University of Delaware*

The SRM-G: Capturing Cognitive Dynamics in Interactive Problem-Solving Tasks. *Yuting Han, Beijing Language and Culture University; Hongyun Liu, Beijing Normal University; PUJUE WANG; Feng Ji, University of Toronto*

Chair: *Yun-Han Weng, The Ohio State University*

69.021. Narratives of Resistance within Education, Past, Present, and Future. Division F - Historical Inquiry in Education; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 306A; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

A historical counterstory of three elementary schools in Pasadena, California, 1900-1920. *Michaela J. López Mares-Tamayo, Polytechnic School*

Methodological Contours and Movidas to Historically Recover the early Maestras of Los Angeles, 1920-1949. *Lluliana Alonso, California State University - Long Beach*

Counternarratives of Chicana/o Librarians from Los Angeles County. *Lorena Camargo Gonzalez, California State University - Sacramento*

Reclaiming Histories of Familial Resistance: The Chicana/Latina Motherscholar-Daughterscholar Phenomenon, 1970s-2020s. *Cindy R. Escobedo, University of California - Los Angeles*

Pilipino Student-Initiated Responses to Exclusion from

Institutional Support: A Counterstory. *Michelle Velasco, University of California - Los Angeles*

Chair: *David G. Garcia, University of California - Los Angeles*

Discussant: *David G. Garcia, University of California - Los Angeles*

69.022. From Classroom to Capitol: Critical Pedagogy and Praxis Under State Repression. Division G - Social Context of Education; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 301B; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Everyone is a Policy Advocate: Seeding the Future of the Education Justice Ecosystem. *Morgan Craven, Intercultural Development Research Association; Celina Moreno, Intercultural Development Research Association; Mikayla Arciaga, Intercultural Development Research Association*
Centering Student Voice: A Case Study of SEAT Advocacy Day. *Yvette Helena Pena Cook, Trinity University; Cameron Samuels, Students Engaged in Advancing Texas; Christianna Thomas, Students Engaged in Advancing Texas*

From Courtroom to Classroom: Critical Pedagogy Through Legal History and State Advocacy. *Habiba Noor, Trinity University*

Policy and Praxis in the Preparation of School Leaders. *Enrique Aleman, Trinity University; Evangeline Aguilera, Trinity University; Morgan Craven, Intercultural Development Research Association*

Chair: *Maria Hantzopoulos, Vassar College*

Discussant: *Maria Hantzopoulos, Vassar College*

69.023. Queering the Social Context of Education. Division G - Social Context of Education; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 303B; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Queering Educational Leadership: Community Colleges, Critical Consciousness, and Systems of Power. *Luis Alberto Legaspi, University of San Diego*

Where are the Black Folx? A Queer Critical Race Theory Intersectional Analysis. *Cleveland Hayes, Indiana University - Indianapolis*

Joteando en el Valle: Drag pedagogy as a playground of Resistance Through QT Joy. *Angel D. Gonzalez, California State University - Fresno*

Flogging Teachers: BDSM, Consent, and the Collapse of Professional Authority. *Roland Sintos Coloma, Wayne State University*

Chair: *Roland Sintos Coloma, Wayne State University*

Discussant: *Cleveland Hayes, Indiana University - Indianapolis*

69.024. Storying Intersectionality for Collective Thriving: Dignity and Wisdom Across Cultures, Generations, Space and Time. Division G - Social Context of Education;

Symposium

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304C;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Creating Space for Cultural Knowledge: How Reflective Practice Enables Immigrant Youth to Recognize, Share, and Connect Across Intersectional Identities. *Rorujorona Ferrell, University of Pennsylvania*

Now You See Me: Unforgetting Exclusionary Histories While Imagining Equitable Postsecondary Futures. *Margot Todman-Mack, University of Pennsylvania*

Queer Filipinx Youth and The Metaphorical Balikbayan Box: Imagining the Possibility of the Return Home to Self. *Anthony Andre Zarate, University of Pennsylvania*

Negotiating Double Diaspora & Identity: Journeys of Indo Caribbean, Afro Caribbean, and Multiracial Educational Leaders. *Regina Hardatt, University of Pennsylvania*

Chair: *Jasmin Esparza Gomez, Duval County Public Schools*

Discussant: *Kesha Bascombe, Malverne High School*

69.025. Division H: Business Meeting Breakfast. Division H - Research, Evaluation and Assessment in Schools; Business Meeting

InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor,
Wilshire Grand Ballroom II; 7:45-9:15am

Chair: *Virginia W. Snodgrass Rangel, University of Houston*

69.026. Critical perspectives on the experiences of students of color. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum G; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Black Mothering in Academia: Sacred Refusal as Resistance, Care, and a Framework for Institutional Change. *Lashante Mystic Briscoe, Northcentral University; Justin L. Alexander, Delaware State University; Karen Holland, Delaware State University; Ashley Grey, Delaware State University*

Black Students with Disabilities and Institutional Terms of Belonging: A Study of Canadian Postsecondary Trajectories. *Tya Collins, University of Ottawa; Ijeoma Aboaja, Ottawa University*

Latinx Spatial Community and Belonging in Higher Education. *Arlyn Y. Moreno Luna, University of California - Los Angeles*

Visualizing UndocuJoy: A Collection of Counterstories from Undocumented Asian Undergraduate Students through Photo Elicitation. *Rose Ann Rico Eborada Gutierrez, University of Nevada - Reno*

Constructing Identity after Mood Disorder Diagnosis: Self, Social, and Institutional Dynamics among Chinese College Students. *Yuting Liang, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Gary Lam, The Chinese University of Hong Kong*

Discussant: *Jerry M. Whitmore, Boston University*

69.027. Data-Driven Insights into Student Retention, Attainment, and Beyond. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum H; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Predicting First-Year Retention in College Using Machine Learning and Traditional Models. *Mario Martinez, University of Houston; Sanga Kim, University of Houston; John Emmons, University of Houston; Caroline Neary, University of Houston*

From Survey to Success: Predicting First-Year Retention Through Longitudinal Data Analysis. *Ting Wang, Rutgers University; Chinyere Ugwuanyi, Rutgers University - New Brunswick; Eduardo Molina, Rutgers University*

Balancing Work and Academics: Undergraduate Student Employment and Outcomes in the University System of Georgia. *Patrick Harris, University System of Georgia; Ethan Christmas, University of Georgia; James M. Byars, University of Georgia; Scott King, University of Georgia; Ju Ran, Columbia University*

Academic Momentum, Financial Aid Dynamics, and Stop-Out Risk: Evidence from Discrete-Time Hazard Models. *John Crooker, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Qingmin Shi, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Christina Drum, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Laurel M. Pritchard, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*

Beyond Earnings: The Multidimensional Job Quality Premiums for University Graduates in European Labour Market. *Sangwoo Lee, University of Warwick; Cesar Burga Idrogo, University College London - IOE*

Chair: *Sora Moon, University of Iowa*

Discussant: *Nicholas A. Bowman, University of Iowa*

69.028. Humanizing Approaches Toward Ethical and Meaningful Student Processes in Higher Education.

Division J - Postsecondary Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum F; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Pathways under Pressure: Migration, Employability, and the Limits of Student Agency. *Muhammad Zulqurnain Ul Haq Qazi, The Ohio State University; Lubna Azram, Sprouts Early Education Center*

Profiling Ethical Sensitivity: A Person-Centered Analysis of Student Judgments on Academic Misconduct. *Liu Liu, University of Georgia; Jin Liu, University of Texas - Arlington; Andrea Jenkins, University of Texas at Arlington; Hongwei Yang, University of West Florida*

“Student Development Theory Had Its Moment”: Exploring the Current Role of SDT in Student Affairs. *Lisa Delacruz Combs, University of North Texas*

“We just can’t make the same kind of connection”: College

Peer Financial Counselors Reflect on Online Versus In-Person Financial Counseling. *Zach Taylor, John Burton Advocates for Youth*

Chair: *Juan Pedro Ross-Olivares, University of California - Los Angeles*

Discussant: *Elizabeth Dunens, University of Minnesota - Rochester*

69.029. Too much of a good thing? How AI is (re)shaping academic careers in higher education. Division J -

Postsecondary Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum I; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Too Much of a Good Thing ? The Curvilinear Effect of Generative AI Usage on Innovative Behavior of Faculty Members in China. *Heng Huang, East China Normal University; Yinqi Ma, Zhejiang Normal University*

Exploring Factors Influencing Faculty Well-Being in GenAI-Enhanced Higher Education Using Machine Learning. *Jiarui Zhao, Shandong University; Jinyu Wang, National Academy of Education Administration; Weitong Liu, Shandong University*

Guiding Graduate Students to Integrate Artificial Intelligence into Qualitative Research Methods: Considerations for Cautious Optimism. *Joanna R. Smith, University of Auckland; Heather McClure, Center for Equity Promotion; Angtola Huy, University of Auckland; Rita Svanks, University of Oregon; Claudia Vincent, University of Oregon*

Imagining Post-Secondary Writing Instruction in a GenAI Future by Researching Alongside Undergraduate Students. *Jennifer Burke Reifman, San Diego State University; Sydney Sullivan, University of California - Davis; Rosabel Ibrahim, San Diego State University*

Discussant: *Nathan Alexander, Howard University*

69.030. Always Becoming: Identity Work in the Making of Teachers. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Plaza III; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Becoming a teacher otherwise: pedagogical imagination of a transmigrant, refugee-background emerging educator. *Jeong Yeon Park, California State University - Fullerton*

Collaborative Pedagogy, Teacher-Becoming and Unbecoming through the Zone of Generativity. *Katy Jeong Cheng Ho Weatherly, University of Macau; Drew Xavier Coles, Teachers College, Columbia University*

“I Always Feel Like I’m Not Doing Enough”: Identity, Emotion, and Beliefs in an ESL Endorsement Program. *Tipsuda Chaomuangkhong, Arizona State University; Aliza Fones, University of Northern Iowa; Doaa Ahmed Ali*

Ibrahim, University of Northern Iowa; Cody Boozell, University of Northern Iowa

Understanding Academic Self-Concepts: Empirical Investigation into Pre-Service Technology Teachers’ Social Comparison Processes and Peer Influences. *Mats Vernholz, Paderborn University; Katrin Temmen, Paderborn University*

Chair: *Jeong Yeon Park, California State University - Fullerton*

Discussant: *Malayna Bernstein, University of Toronto*

69.031. Cultivating Caminata Pedagogies: Teaching and Learning while Walking with Emplaced and Embodied Knowledges in Texas. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Symposium

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 3; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Cultivating Caminata Pedagogies: Teaching and Learning while Walking with Emplaced and Embodied Knowledges in Texas. *Marial Quezada, University of Texas at Austin; Celine Vallejo Norman, The University of Texas at Austin; Patricia Nuñez, University of Texas at Austin; Leticia Garza, University of Texas at Austin*

Title: Collaborating Native Plant caminata, Planting Pedagogical Possibilities Beyond Colonial and Censored Curriculum. *Marial Quezada, University of Texas at Austin*
Exploring Approaches to Caring and the Affective Dimensions of Racial Geography Walks. *Celine Vallejo Norman, The University of Texas at Austin*

As We Walk Together: caminata to Reveal and Remember. *Patricia Nuñez, University of Texas at Austin*

Place-based “Wondering Walks” to Translanguage in/with The Land’s Semiotic Resources for Science Education. *Leticia Garza, University of Texas at Austin*

Chair: *Luis Urrieta, University of Texas at Austin*

Discussant: *Luis Urrieta, University of Texas at Austin*

69.032. Insights from Examining and Comparing Elementary Teachers’ Visions Across Content Areas. Division K -

Teaching and Teacher Education; Symposium

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 6; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Elementary Teachers’ Visions for Student Learning in Mathematics and ELA. *Rebecca Memmolo, University of Delaware; Olga Hawranick, Washington State University; Blake Nelson, Washington State University; Anne Garrison Wilhelm, Southern Methodist University*

Examining Elementary Teachers’ Instructional Visions for Mathematics and ELA in Context. *Rebecca Memmolo, University of Delaware*

Seeing and Doing: The Relationship Between Elementary Teachers’ Instructional Vision and Practice within Classroom Discussion. *Amy Guillotte, University of*

Pennsylvania; Sam Prough, University of Delaware; Rebecca Memmolo, University of Delaware; Anne Garrison Wilhelm, Southern Methodist University; Sarah Schneider Kavanagh, University of Pennsylvania; Robyn K. Pinilla, University of Texas - El Paso; Lynsey K. Gibbons, University of Delaware

Chair: *Anne Garrison Wilhelm, Southern Methodist University*

Discussant: *Margaret Vaughn, Washington State University*

69.033. Roots, Thorns and Shoots: Cultivating Teacher Perspectives to Reimagine Teaching for Collective Liberation. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Structured Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 515A;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

1. K-12 Educators of Color Enact Multiliterate Curricula to Create Reciprocal Learning Environments for Multilingual Students (Poster 1). *Ying-Tung Lin, University of Texas at Austin*
2. What uproots teachers: Rehumanizing the Profession: Understanding Teacher Attrition Through the Lens of Humanization (Poster 2). *Gaëlle Mounioloux, University of Washington*
3. For Teachers by Teachers: Reflections from Teacher Leaders of Color Staying Rooted in EduDesign Communities (Poster 3). *Andrea Carreno Cortez, University of Washington; Janaki Nagarajan; Maria-Elena Velasquez, Lake Washington School District; Kaity Cassio Faye, Seattle Public Schools; Mark Juaton, Seattle Public Schools; Khadijah Ladd, Seattle Public Schools; Courtney Wiley, Highline Public Schools*
4. Empowered Educators: Teacher Leadership as a Pathway for Collective Liberation - Seattle's Teacher Leadership Cadre (Poster 4). *Nichole Lau, University of Washington*
5. Exploring the Experiences of K-12 Vietnamese Language Teachers (Poster 5). *Pauline Dong, California State University - Long Beach*
6. The connection between the behaviors of school administrators and teacher job satisfaction (Poster 6). *Beth Ann Thompson, University of Washington*
7. This Is Why I'm Here: Instructional Leadership for Authentic Change for Equity (Poster 7). *Kris Hill, University of Washington*
8. Navigating In the Shadows: (In)Visibly Racially Hostile Work Environments and Impacts on Asian American Teachers (Poster 8). *Leslie A. Saito, Long Beach Unified School District*
9. Supporting Diversity: Job Satisfaction and Intent to Stay of Special Education Teachers of Color (Poster 9). *Shivani Oberoi, University of Washington*

Chair: *Betina Hsieh, University of Washington*

Discussant: *Sylvia Stralberg Bagley, University of Washington*

69.034. Dual Language Immersion Programs in LAUSD and the Potential for Equitable Learning Opportunities. Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 1;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Dual Language Immersion Programs within LAUSD Elementary Schools: Who Do They Enroll? *Erica Frankenberg, Pennsylvania State University; Sarah Asson, Education Northwest; Clemence Darriet, University of California - Los Angeles; Lucrecia Santibanez, University of California - Los Angeles; Claudia G. Cervantes-Soon, Arizona State University; Francesca López, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Do Dual Language Programs Lead to Increased School Enrollment? Examining the Relationship Between Program Founding and Enrollment. *Clemence Darriet, University of California - Los Angeles; Lucrecia Santibanez, University of California - Los Angeles; Erica Frankenberg, Pennsylvania State University; Sarah Asson, Education Northwest; Claudia G. Cervantes-Soon, Arizona State University; Francesca López, University of Wisconsin - Madison*
Enrollment Patterns and Online Portrayals of Dual Language Programs. *Francesca López, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Clemence Darriet, University of California - Los Angeles; Lucrecia Santibanez, University of California - Los Angeles; Claudia G. Cervantes-Soon, Arizona State University; Sarah Asson, Education Northwest; Erica Frankenberg, Pennsylvania State University*

Can DLI Fulfill the Promise of Bilingual Instruction for English Learners? *Lucrecia Santibanez, University of California - Los Angeles; Clemence Darriet, University of California - Los Angeles; Sarah Asson, Education Northwest; Erica Frankenberg, Pennsylvania State University; Francesca López, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Claudia G. Cervantes-Soon, Arizona State University*

Chair: *Claudia G. Cervantes-Soon, Arizona State University*

Discussant: *Ilana M. Umansky, University of Oregon*

69.035. Mitigating Financial Barriers for Teaching Candidates: Federal, State, and Local Approaches to Service Scholarships. Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 2;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Financing Teacher Preparation: A National Landscape of Needs and Policy Solutions. *Wesley Wei, Learning Policy Institute*
Financial Aid for Future Educators: Assessing a Federal Grant's Impact on Student's Postsecondary Decisions. *Wesley Morris, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*
California's Golden State Teacher Grant Program. *Melanie Leung-Gagné, Learning Policy Institute; Desiree Carver-Thomas, Learning Policy Institute; Maria Maria Castillo,*

Vanderbilt University; Cicely Bingener, University of California - Los Angeles; Susan Kemper Patrick, Learning Policy Institute; María Virginia Giani, University of Florida
The University of Wisconsin's Teacher Pledge. *Nicholas Hillman, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Kathryn Boonstra, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Jared D. Colston, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Chair: *Susan Kemper Patrick, Learning Policy Institute*

Discussants: *Annamarie M. Francois, University of California - Los Angeles; Thomas Owenby, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

69.036. Politics and Policies of Threat: Detention, De-authorization, and Disappearance of Pk-20 Immigrant & International Students. Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 10; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

The Social Construction of Immigration Status: Historical Foundations and Contemporary Implications. *Liliana E. Castrellon, San José State University; Alonso R. Reyna Rivarola, Salt Lake Community College*

Palpable Fear: Schools with newcomer students responding to the second Trump Administration. *Diego A Mureno, Chapel Hill-Carrboro City Schools*

Mobility Under Watch: Power, Policy, and the Global South Student. *Eunice Laryea, Miami University (OH); Abisola Aminat Adegunju, Miami University (OH)*

The Failure of Leadership Standards to Support Undocumented Students in an Era of Political Hostility and Vitriol. *Érica Fernández, Miami University (OH); Gerardo R. López, Michigan State University; Marina López, University of California - Los Angeles*

Responsibility to Whom? Leadership (in)Actions Amid Targeting of International and Immigrant University Students. *Samantha P. Scribner, Miami University (OH); Eunice Laryea, Miami University (OH); Abisola Aminat Adegunju, Miami University (OH)*

Chair: *Samantha P. Scribner, Miami University (OH)*

Discussant: *Liliana E. Castrellon, San José State University*

SIG Sessions

69.037. Gentrification 3.0 in Dual Language Bilingual Education: A Districtwide Analysis of Equity for Emergent Bilinguals. SIG-Bilingual Education Research; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 303A; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Constructing Access, Reproducing Inequity: Equity Traps in Educator and Institutional Discourses in DLBE. *Santiago*

Parra Giraldo, Purdue University; Tirtha Karki, Purdue University; Dafne Zanelli, Purdue University
"Survival" Versus "Curiosity" in DLBE: A Latina Principal's Use of Interest Convergence with the White Listening Subject. *Priya M Dabak, Purdue University; Vikrant Chap, Purdue University*

Instrumental Rationality in Dual Language Contexts: Administrator Discourse and Praxis. *Kelly J. Farkas, Purdue University; Samarnh Pang, Purdue University*

Addressing Gentrification and Critical Consciousness in Dual Language Bilingual Education Programs. *Alejandro Baquero-Sierra, Purdue University; Yangyang Zhu, Purdue University*

Semiotic Landscape Gentrification. *Garrett Delavan, University of New Mexico; Trish Morita-Mullaney, Purdue University; Juan A. Freire, Brigham Young University*

Chair: *Garrett Delavan, University of New Mexico*

Discussant: *Juan A. Freire, Brigham Young University*

69.038. Identifying and Supporting Multilingual Learners Across Systems and Classrooms. SIG-Bilingual Education Research; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 301A; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Referral Processes for English Learners to Special Education: A Survey of General Education Teachers. *Phoebe J Ahn, Vanderbilt University; Jeannette Mancilla-Martinez, Vanderbilt University; Jason C. Chow, Vanderbilt University*
Multilingual Educators Making Sense of Theory, Research, and Controversy in a Bilingual Endorsement Program. *Patrick Proctor, Boston College; Qinghua Liu, Boston College; Brenda Luo, Boston College; Aaron Talbot Kennedy Coleman, Bridgewater State University*

Disentangling Language and Disability: Exploring Special Education Eligibility by Language Status. *Brianna Yamakasi, Emory University; Min Hyun Oh, United States Department of Defense; Gigi Luk, McGill University*

Understanding Waived English Learners (ELs): EL Service Opt-Out Patterns in Utah Elementary Schools. *Natalia Palacios, University of Virginia; Bethany A. Bell, University of Virginia; Min Hyun Oh, United States Department of Defense; Natalie L. Bohlmann, Montana State University - Billings*

Spanish-English within and across languages predictions of reading risk based on English proficiency and language of instruction. *Julian M. Siebert, University of California - San Francisco; Lillian Durán, University of Oregon; Monica Pilar Zegers, University of California - San Francisco; Francesca Pei, University of California - San Francisco; Marilu Tempini, University of California - San Francisco*

Chair: *Julie A. Washington, University of California - Irvine*

Discussant: *Dianna R. Townsend, University of Nevada - Reno*

69.039. Career and Technical Education Student Outcomes.

SIG-Career & Technical Education and Workplace Learning; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 8;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Evaluating Long-Term Effects of Secondary Career and Technical Education Concentration on Postsecondary and Wage Outcomes. *Zhonghan Xie, University of Michigan*
Closing the Gap: Career Clusters and Workforce Returns in Texas. *Angela Crevar, Mercer University; Jennifer A. Freeman, Texas Tech University; Jacob Kirksey, Texas Tech University*
Postsecondary and Workforce Outcomes after Participation in Nevada CTE Programs. *Federick Ngo, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Xue Xing, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Monique North, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*
Examining the Relationship between Academy Theme in High School and Postsecondary Major of NAF Graduates. *Edward C. Fletcher, The Ohio State University; In Heok Lee, University of Georgia; Nicholas Minar, NAF*
Field-of-Study Mismatch and Skill Use: Mitigating Wage Penalties in Knowledge-Based Sectors. *Seong Ji Jeong, Pennsylvania State University; Mihee Park, Auburn University; Xue Xing, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*
Chair: *Katherine Hughes, EdWordian, LLC*
Discussant: *Oscar A. Aliaga, University of South Florida*

69.040. Students with Disabilities in School Voucher Programs.

SIG-Charter & School Choice; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 7;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Private School Vouchers and Special Education: A Legal Perspective. *Paul O'Neil, Barton Gilman; Charisse A. Gulosino, University of Memphis*
A Policy Review of Voucher Programs (Dis)Serving Students with Disabilities. *David E. DeMatthews, University of Texas at Austin; Torri Danny Hart, University of Texas at Austin; David S. Knight, University of Washington; Daniel Geist, University of Texas at Austin*
School Vouchers and Students with Disabilities: A Systematic Literature Review. *Federico R. Waitoller, University of Illinois at Chicago; Charisse A. Gulosino, University of Memphis*
Unforgetting the history of school vouchers: A Disability Critical Race Theory analysis of what the market can do for education. *Kathleen M. Collins, Pennsylvania State University; James Collins, Pennsylvania State University*
Chair: *Federico R. Waitoller, University of Illinois at Chicago*
Discussant: *Maria Lewis, Pennsylvania State University*

69.041. How Schools Make Race: Teaching Latinx Racialization. SIG-Critical Examination of Race, Ethnicity,

Class and Gender in Education; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Atrium II;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Introduction to Study: How Schools Make Race: Teaching Latinx Racialization. *Laura Chavez-Moreno, University of California - Los Angeles*
The Study's Race Theory in Education. *Zeus Leonardo, University of California - Berkeley*
The Study and Bilingual Education and Latinx Racialization. *Maria Cioe-Pena, University of Pennsylvania*
Chair: *Angela Valenzuela, University of Texas at Austin*
Discussant: *Angela Valenzuela, University of Texas at Austin*

69.042. Critical Methodological Innovations in Quantitative Research. SIG-Critical Quantitative Methodologies; Paper Session

InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Echo Park; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

How Multilevel Modeling Techniques Underestimate the Effects of Racial Oppression. *Mike K. Russell, Boston College; Daniel Raphael, Boston College*
Hybridity at Play: Imagining New Methodological Futures for Critical Quantitative Inquiry. *John Matthew Fredericks, Arizona State University*
Latent Stories, Latent Space: Unsupervised Discovery Methods for Educational Counternarratives. *Christopher Irwin, Florida International University; Remy Dou, Florida International University; Sue Sunbury, Harvard University; Philip M. Sadler, Harvard University; Gerhard Sonnert, Harvard University*
MNLFA as a CritQuant Psychometric Tool. *David F. Feldon, Utah State University; Umar Shehzad, Utah State University*
The Application of Multilevel Modeling in QuantCrit and CritQuant Frameworks: A Critical-MLM Approach (CritMLM). *Jeffrey Shero, Vanderbilt University; Mason Shero, Denison University; Andres Pinedo, Vanderbilt University; Jessica Logan, Vanderbilt University*
Chair: *Mellie Torres*

69.043. Exploring the Potential of Artificial Intelligence in Early Childhood Education. SIG-Early Education and Child Development; Symposium

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Georgia I;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Navigating AI in Early Childhood Education: Ethical Challenges, Opportunities, and Implications for Higher Education Practice. *Annie White, California State University - Channel Islands; Lauren Chase, CSU Channel Islands*
Utilizing AI in Pre-service Teachers' Learning of Multicultural Instruction. *Chenyi Zhang, Georgia State University; Lauren Margulieux, Georgia State University*

AI Education for Young Children: Considerations for Designing an AI Curriculum and Strategies in Early Childhood Education. *Joohee Lee, University of Texas - Arlington*

Chair: *Lynn E. Cohen, Long Island University - C.W. Post Campus*
Discussant: *Sohyun Meacham, University of Northern Iowa*

69.044. Graduate Student Success: Mentoring, Identity, & Institutional Change. SIG-Graduate and Postdoctoral Education across the Disciplines; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 9;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Cultivating Courage: Identity Alignment and Personal Growth in a Social Justice EdD Program. *Violet Ballard, San Francisco State University; Barbara A. Henderson, San Francisco State University; Chu Hsi Tseng, San Francisco State University; Robert Gabriner, San Francisco State University*

Engaged Individuals, Lagging Institutions: Exploring Interdisciplinary Work in Chilean Doctoral Education. *Ivet M. Parra-Gaete, University of Arizona; Sergio Celis, Universidad de Chile*

Frequency-Quality Paradox in China: The Supervisor-Student Relationship and Graduate Students' Academic Pressure from the Perspective of Horizontal Stratification in Higher Education. *Jingjing Wang, Nanjing University*

Discussant: *Veronique W. Merritt, Brigham Young University*

69.045. Margins, Gutters, and Futures: Comics as Sites of Critical Literacy and Speculative Cultural Resistance. SIG-Media, Culture, and Learning; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Georgia II;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Pedagogies of Hope in the Shadow of The Empire: Reimagining Learning through Speculative Fiction. *Michael B. Dando, St. Cloud State University*

Unrepresentability as an Affordance in Comics About Transition. *David E. Low, California State University - Fresno*

Surrendering to Care: Black Canary and a mother/daughter pedagogy of loss. *Dani Friedrich, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Too Many Abs: Narrative Inquiry of Critical Noticings Across Comic and Anime Conventions. *Karis Michelle Jones, Baylor University*

Speculative Curriculum: Epistemology, The Human & Eve Ewing's Monica Rambeau: Photon. *Sarah Ishmael, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Chair: *Larry C. Bryant, Metro State University*

Discussant: *Lauren Leigh Kelly, Rutgers University*

69.046. Sociocultural Origins and Processes of Student

Motivation: Advancing Theory, Informing Research, and Transforming Practice. SIG-Motivation in Education; Symposium

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Beaudry A; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Racializing Motivation: A Race-Reimagined Framework of Belonging, Emoting, and Achieving Within the STEM Education Context. *Jessica T. Decuir-Gunby, University of Southern California; Saba Lily Modaresi, University of Southern California; Paul A. Schutz, University of Arizona*

The Politics of Goal Regulation: Race, Power, and Student Aspirations. *Akane Zusho, Fordham University; Revathy Kumar, University of Toledo*

Exploring the Sociocultural Dynamics of Self-Efficacy Development. *Ellen L. Usher, Mayo Clinic; Xiao-Yin Chen, University of Tennessee*

A Complexity Perspective on Culture, Identity, and Motivation: The Dynamic Systems Model of Role Identity. *Avi Kaplan, Temple University; Joanna K. Garner, Old Dominion University*

Cultural Insights: The Motivation Paradox of East Asian Learners. *Mimi Bong, Korea University; Dayeon Jeong, Korea University - Brain and Motivation Research Institute; Seohee Park, Korea University - Brain and Motivation Research Institute; Jiwon Kim, Korea University - Brain and Motivation Research Institute; Jimin Suh, Korea University - Brain and Motivation Research Institute; Suyeon Gena Kim, Korea University - Brain and Motivation Research Institute; Jenny Chaehyun Park, Korea University - Brain and Motivation Research Institute*

Toward an Interpersonal Theory of Academic Motivation: Rethinking Student Motivation Through an Interdependent Self Lens. *Gregory Arief D. Liem, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University*

Chairs: *Gregory Arief D. Liem, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University; Mimi Bong, Korea University*

69.047. Artificial Intelligence in Online Teaching and Learning. SIG-Online Teaching and Learning; Paper Session

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Palos Verdes; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Does AI Use Influence Students' Academic Performance Directly and Indirectly Through Mental Health? *Sunha Kim, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

AI-Supported Forums and the Paradox of Social Presence: A Mixed-Methods Study Using the CoI Framework. *Sophia Soomin Lee, University of Florida; Jason DeLeon, University of Florida; Rob Moore, University of Florida; Jinnie Shin, University of Florida*

AI Co-Tutors and Instructor Adaptation in Online Classrooms: Evolving Roles and Teaching Practices. *Kimberley L.*

Chandler, Johns Hopkins University; Kathryn N. Thompson, Johns Hopkins Center for Talented Youth

Making AI Use Ethical, Visible, and Transparent: Student Perceptions of AI Assessment Scale (AIAS) Integrated Online Course Design. *Selcuk Dogan, Georgia Southern University; Nihan Agacli Dogan, Georgia Southern University*

Chair: *Rick J. Voithofer, The Ohio State University*

69.048. New Frameworks, Methods, and Teaching Strategies for Understanding and Addressing Emotions in Mathematics Classrooms. SIG-Research in Mathematics Education; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum A; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

The Emotionally Responsive Elementary Mathematics Model: A Framework for Understanding and Addressing Emotions in Mathematics Learning Opportunities. *Leigh McLean, University of Delaware*

A Set of Equitable Mathematics Teaching Practices That Respond to Students' Emotions. *Jonee Wilson, University of Virginia; Erica Litke, University of Delaware; Miriam Simone Leshin, University of Virginia; Samantha Akridge, University of Delaware*

Building Mathematics Classroom Connectedness Through Dialogue. *Jessica Pierson Bishop, Texas State University*
Errorful Learning as Supports for Mathematics Learning & Motivation. *Christina Areizaga Barbieri, University of Delaware; Elena Silla, University of Delaware*

The Role of Emotional Validation in Math Classrooms. *Gerardo Ramirez, Ball State University; Daeun Park, Sungkyunkwan University*

Incorporating Rough Drafts and Revising into Mathematics Teaching to Support Students with Taking Intellectual Risks. *Amanda Jansen, University of Delaware; Leigh McLean, University of Delaware; Christina Areizaga Barbieri, University of Delaware*

Chair: *Leigh McLean, University of Delaware*

Discussant: *Amanda Jansen, University of Delaware*

69.049. Reimagining K–12 Disciplinary Literacy: Access, Engagement, and Innovation Across Subjects. SIG-Research in Reading and Literacy; Structured Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 515B; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

1. Using Metalanguage to Support Writing in Mathematics (Poster 1). *Michelle Nguyen Kwok, Texas A&M University*
2. Transmodalising Multiliteracies Pedagogy for Multilingual Learners' Science Learning Leveraging Infographics (Poster 2). *Sujin Kim, George Mason University; Xiaowen Chen, George Mason University; Eden Langston, George Mason University; Kathleen Ramos, George Mason University*

3. Writing Apprenticeship: A Framework for Equitable, Disciplinary Writing Instruction (Poster 3). *Jenell Krishnan, WestEd; Menya Cole, WestEd*
4. Moving Meaning: Expanding Science Literacies with Body Movement (Poster 4). *Amanda R. Diaz, California State University - Fullerton; Rebecca Woodard, University of Illinois at Chicago; Maria Varelas, University of Illinois Chicago; Stephanie Batres Spezza, University of Illinois at Chicago; Roman Rock, University of Illinois at Chicago; Nathan C. Phillips, University of Illinois at Chicago; Rachele Tsachor, University of Illinois at Chicago*
5. State Policy Approaches to Disciplinary Literacy: Learning from Colorado, Michigan, and Oregon (Poster 5). *Rachel Grimes Tripathy, WestEd; Amanda Nabors, WestEd; Edrick Willie Borja Sabalburo, WestEd*
6. A Both/And Approach: Supporting Students with Reading Disabilities in Disciplinary Literacy (Poster 6). *Elizabeth Zagata, WestEd*
7. Disciplinary Literacy for Young Monolingual and Multilingual Learners (Poster 7). *Lisa Domke, Georgia State University; Tanya S. Wright, University of Michigan; Amelia Wenk Gotwals, Michigan State University*
8. Noticing for Equity in Disciplinary Literacy (Poster 8). *Danny C. Martinez, University of California - Davis; Alexis Patterson Williams, University of California - Davis*
9. Young Learners Thinking Science (Poster 9). *Pamela A. Mason, Harvard University*
10. Piloting a Disciplinary Literacy Focused Curriculum for Striving Readers: Reading Apprenticeship for Academic Literacy Learning (Poster 10). *Misty Sailors, WestEd; Heather Howlett, WestEd*
11. Mapping the Evidence Base: A Scoping Review of Disciplinary Literacy Research in K-12 Education (Poster 11). *Aaron Soo Ping Chow, WestEd; Thomas Torre Gibney, WestEd; Jazmin T. Cruz, WestEd*

Chair: *Misty Sailors, WestEd*

Discussant: *Zhihui Fang, University of Florida*

69.050. Women Sustaining Each Other. SIG-Research on Women and Education; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 306B; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

- Becoming the Capital: Black Women's Identity and the Dual Work of Community Cultural Wealth. *Ashley Houston, Missouri State University; Zakiyah Willis, Missouri State University; Jordan Allen, Missouri State University; Kathryn Plautz, Missouri State University*
- Writing Ourselves into Academia: An Autoethnography of Female Academics Reimagining Scholarly Progress through Writing Retreats. *Stephanie M Branson, Northern Arizona University; Marti Canipe, Northern Arizona University; Heather Lindfors-Navarro, Northern Arizona University; Victoria Damjanovic, Northern Arizona University*

The “Sister Circle” as Peer Mentorship for Black Women on the Academic Job Market. *CoCo Massengale, Stanford University; Sandra Habtamu, Foothill College; Kyalamboka Brown, Stanford University*

Paths Aren’t Linear: Imagining the Future of a Collective of Women. *Shannon Athey, West Chester University of Pennsylvania; Hyunjeong Lee, Indiana University; Jessica McClain, Indiana University; Dianne T. Wellington, SUNY - College at Cortland; Jill A. Scott, Indiana University; Sharon Daley, Indiana University; Shaunta D Scroggins, Purdue University; Breanya Hogue, Purdue University*

Chair: *Lauren P. Bailes, University of Delaware*

69.051. Negotiating Belonging and Mobility in Rural Education: Family, Community, and Context. SIG-Rural Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum B; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Cultivating Learning and Social Capital for Educational Futures in a Rural Migrant Family. *Lin Deng, University of Florida; Alice Hsun-Fang Hsu, Harvard University*

‘I’ll Appreciate It Later’: Taking Rural Capitals to College and Beyond. *Wendy Pfrenger, University of Mississippi*

Parents in Rural Communities During an Ongoing Displacement Crisis: The Bioecological Model as a Theoretical Framework. *Yael Grinshtain, Tel-Hai College*
Staying or Leaving? Unforgetting Rural Students’ Aspirations and Opportunities. *Alicia Francisca Noreiga, Acadia University*

“The Village Chooses Us”: Rural Becoming Across Generations and Species in Post-Soviet Kazakhstan. *Dilraba Anayatova, Arizona State University*

Discussant: *Sarah J Zuckerman, University of Nebraska - Lincoln*

69.052. Quantitative and Mixed Methods Research in Social Studies Education. SIG-Social Studies Research; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Atrium I; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Measuring Racial and Gender Representation in YouTube Instructional Videos using Natural Language Processing (NLP). *Cody C. Pritchard, University of Tennessee; Hadi Bhidya, University of Tennessee; Joshua Rosenberg, University of Tennessee; Gregory D. Peterson, University of Tennessee*

Insufficient Support or Insufficient Research? A Review of Professional Development for Novice Social Studies Teachers. *Alexa M. Quinn, James Madison University; Anna Yonas, University of Kansas*

Who Teaches Urban Social Studies? A Critical Demographic Analysis. *Amy E. Allen, Virginia Tech; Thomas O. Williams, Virginia Tech; David Hicks, Virginia Tech*

The Dynamics of Empathy: A Quantitative Ethnography of Student Discursive Moves in Social Studies Discussions. *Ariana Zetlin, University of Pennsylvania; Joseph Eisman, Purdue University*

Pedagogical Responsiveness and Sensitivity as Mediators: Exploring Cultural Perceptions and Research Intentions Among Social Studies Teachers. *Chenchen Lu, Purdue University; Kathryn M. Obenchain, Purdue University*

Chair: *Chenchen Lu, Purdue University*

Discussant: *Patience Amadu, University of Colorado - Colorado Springs*

69.053. Unforgetting the Past, Disrupting the Present: Border-Crossing Approaches to Inclusive Education Policy, Research, and Practice. SIG-Special and Inclusive Education Research; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum J; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Constructing the Fifth World: Metacognitive-Cultural-Linguistic-Emotive-Affective Mediational Borders in Reading Comprehension with Emergent Bilinguals with Disabilities. *Sarah M. Salinas, Minnesota State University - Mankato; David I. Hernandez-Saca, University of Northern Iowa*

Addressing Disproportionality in Special Education through Pragmatic Language Research on African American Vernacular English (AAVE). *Camille O’Quin, Governors State University*

Latinx Immigrant Families in the Educational Borderlands: Towards Transformative Ruptures in Family Engagement in Special Education. *Argelia Lara, Santa Clara University; Pedro E. Nava, Santa Clara University; Mirsha Gomez, Oakland United School District*

Living, Teaching, and Resisting at the Margins: A Transnational Autoethnography of Disability, Crisis, and Policy Disruption. *Suman Rath, Montclair State University*
Nuancing Racial Identity: Uniting Critical Race Theory and Gee’s Theory of Identity. *William A. Proffitt, Montclair State University; Courtney L. Wilt, University of Wisconsin - Whitewater; Inna Stepaniuk, Simon Fraser University*

Redrawing Educational Borders: Reimagining Eligibility and Placement of Students with Disabilities in Dual Language Programs. *Dionne L. Davis, Texas State University; Xinxia Li, The George Washington University*

Chairs: *Inna Stepaniuk, Simon Fraser University; Dosun Ko, Santa Clara University*

Discussant: *Dosun Ko, Santa Clara University*

Division and SIG Roundtables

69.054. AERA Roundtable Session Saturday 7:45 am;
Roundtable Session

69.054-1. Examining Leadership's Direct and Indirect Effects on Student Outcomes (Table 1). Division A - Administration; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

- Performing Inclusion, Withholding Power: Digital Representations of Student Board Members. *Betul Ozel, University of Arizona; Melanie Bertrand, University of Arizona; Chi Nguyen, University of Arizona; Joonkil Ahn, University of Arizona*
- Exploring School Leadership's Influence on Student Achievement: Machine Learning insights from Missouri's Largest Teacher Evaluation System. *Xintong Li, University of Missouri; Thomas Hairston, University of Missouri*
- Examining the heterogeneity of relationship between principal leadership, organizational process, and student achievement across school contexts: A multigroup multilevel structural equation model approach. *Huang Wu, University of Missouri - Kansas City; Sijia Zhang, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Jacob M. Marszalek, University of Missouri - Kansas City*

Equity Centered Practices that Support Marginalized Subgroup Success. *Kenneth R. Ward, Broward County Public Schools; Maysaa Y. Barakat, Florida Atlantic University*

Chair: *Maria Boeke Mongillo, Central Connecticut State University*

69.054-2. Healing the Healers: Leader Wellbeing as Radical Act (Table 2). Division A - Administration; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

- Stress and Resilience Factors among Arizona's K-12 Education Leaders. *Ashley K. Vaughan, Northern Arizona University*
- Futuring Black Male Administrators' Wholeness: Cultivating Principal Wellness and Transformative Leadership in K-12 Schools. *Curtis Levern Lewis, Michigan State University; Randolph Hull, plymouth canton community schools; Jason McGhee, Grand Rapids Public Schools; Dominic Knighten, Holt Junior High School; Dorinda Carter Andrews, Michigan State University*
- Psychological Safety of School Administrators: Invisible Barriers. *Fei Wang, University of British Columbia*
- From Principal to Teacher: The Contagious Relationship Between Stress and Occupational Well-Being. *Yi Sun, National Institute of Education, Nanyang Technological University; Hongbiao Yin, The Chinese University of Hong Kong*

Chair: *Ishmael Miller, Arizona State University*

69.054-3. Leadership in Transition: Navigating Context,

Community Engagement, and Equity Challenges (Table 3). Division A - Administration; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

- Between Vision and Reality: Safety Strategies and Implementation Challenges in Chicago Schools. *Christina Scanlon, University of Chicago; David Wilson Johnson, Northwestern University; Rebecca Hinze-Pifer, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Clarice Robinson, University of Chicago*
- Leading with Insight: Principals' Community Knowledge and Policy Action for Multilingual Learners. *Andrea Louise Ochoa, Brown University; Jae Won Claire Shin, Johns Hopkins University; Rebecca A. Cruz, Johns Hopkins University*
- Suburbia's Shifting Landscape: Educational Leadership in Demographic Transformation. *Davis Clement, Eastern Michigan University; Margaret Thornton, Rowan University*
- Teachers as community leaders: Extending the Community Equity Literacy (CEL) framework beyond school administrators. *Holly Marcolina, SUNY Potsdam*

Chair: *Jeff Walls, University of Iowa*

69.054-4. Curriculum as Ceremony: Storying Memory, Resistance, and Liberatory Futures (Table 4). Division B - Curriculum Studies; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

- Dreaming From my Abuela's Arms: Pedagogies of Love. *Daniela Reyes Puente, Purdue University*
- Lighting Life's Fire: A Reflection on Ritual, Resistance, and Rebirth. *Miguel Mendoza, University of Texas - Rio Grande Valley*
- Mapping the Middle: Currere Counter-Stories Excavating Carceral Genealogies and Bridging Toward Liberatory School Futures. *Guadalupe Elena Ramirez, Chicago Public Schools; Steven R. Flores, Chicago Public Schools; Kyndall Jackson, Youth Teams in Education Research; Breanna Lopez, Youth Teams in Education Research; Dulce Gonzalez, Youth Teams in Education Research; Aayla Holiday, Thornton Fractional South*
- (Re)membering: Storying Through the Weaponization of Curriculum and Memory. *Gina English Tillis, The University of Memphis; Anna Falkner, University of Memphis; Crystal Cook, University of Memphis*

Chair: *Jonggeun Park, Teachers College, Columbia University*

69.054-5. Critical Curricular Inquiries in Precarious Times: Student Agency, Transformations, and Place (Table 5). Division B - Curriculum Studies; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

- Integrating Brazilian Cordel Literature in the Canadian Childhood Classroom. *Nikki Rotas, Western University*
- Interrogating the “Goodness” Of the “Good School” By Analyzing the Curriculum of White Ignorance. *Briana Markoff, University of Maine at Farmington*
- Middle School Students’ Civic Engagement in Fraught Political Times and Places. *Samuel Burmester, University of California - Santa Cruz; Rachel Talbert, Teachers College, Columbia University*
- Student Transformation Through Place-Based Education's Windows, Mirrors, and Doorways. *Kim Megyesi-Brem, Claremont Graduate University; Guan Saw, Claremont Graduate University; Ryan Culbertson, Texas Tech University; Paola Rosenberg, Claremont Graduate University; Jesus Gonzalez, University of Texas - Pan American*

Chair: *Laura M. Jewett, University of Texas - Rio Grande Valley*

69.054-6. Reimagining Community-Based Educational Research (Table 6). Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

- Change for what? Understanding youth notions of environmental justice in an urban neighborhood context. *Lisa D. Nehring, Johns Hopkins University; Richard Lofton, Johns Hopkins University*
- Cocinar, Crear, Contar: Storytelling and Futuring in Food-related Learning Design. *Maria Jose Anderson-Coto, UC Irvine; Alejandra Gallegos, Santa Ana Early Learning Initiative; Wendy Giovanna Gomez, Santa Ana Early Learning Initiative; Kevin Crowley, University of Pittsburgh; Andres Sebastian Bustamante, University of California - Irvine; Diana Leyva, University of Pittsburgh*
- Imagining Spaces for Social Justice Literacies: Developments in a Community-Based Discourse Community. *Ashley Summer Boyd, Washington State University; Rachael Wolney, Illinois State University*
- “Our Streets (Too)”: The Role of Organizing Scholarship in Community-Based Research. *Naomi Mae W., University of Wisconsin - Madison; David C. Turner III, University of California, Los Angeles*

Chair: *Rachel McMillian, Indiana University - Indianapolis*

69.054-7. Reimagining Educational Research for and with Asian Americans (Table 7). Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

- Beyond Perpetual Foreigners: Racial Experiences of Korean American Families Across Generations. *Jinhee Kim,*

Kennesaw State University; Sophia Han, University of South Florida

Resisting English Dominance: The Narrative Inquiry of Heritage Language Schools in Los Angeles. *Jiyun Yu, University of California - Los Angeles; Kathy Yi-Hang LI, UCLA*

Telling my Grandmother's Stories: Filipina/x/o American History, Community Museums, and the Labor of Repair. *Paulina Fraser, University of Michigan*

The Academic Journey of Bangladeshi Americans in Higher Education: Understanding their College Major Decision Making. *Ramisa Maliha Chowdhury, Claremont Graduate University*

Chair: *Wenyang Sun, University of Utah*

69.054-8. Assemblages, Realities And Tensions In Decolonizing Education (Table 8). SIG-Decolonial, Postcolonial, and Anti-Colonial Studies in Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

- Analysis of Instagram’s Algorithm on #decolonizeeducation. *Andrew Flanagan, Teachers College, Columbia University*
- The Paradox of Language Use in Kenya’s Education System: A Deepening Divide Between Policy, Practice, and Sociocultural Realities. *Jackson Mainai Shaa, Texas Tech University*
- Beyond Risk and Safety: Toward a Fanonian Theory of Pedagogical Ungovernability. *Omi Salas-SantaCruz, University of Utah*
- Bridging Epistemologies: Unforgetting the Past to Imagine Plural Futures in Literacy Research. *David Bwire, The College of New Jersey*
- Historicizing “Terrortory” from the Bay to LA: Violence as Socialization in Contemporary Settler Colonial California. *Theresa Burruel Stone, Sonoma State University*

69.054-9. Teachers as Agents of Change in Sustainability Education (Table 9). SIG-Environmental Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

- Effects of Cognitive and Affective Narrative Framings in Teaching the Climate and Nature Emergency. *Kevin J. Holohan, Grand Valley State University; Josie Holohan, Northwestern University*
- Philosophies and Practices of Garden-Based Educators: A Mixed-Methods Study. *Scott Morrison, Elon University; Grace Rasmussen, Elon University*
- (Re)thinking Climate Change and Sustainability Education: A Case Study of Junior High Schools in Ghana. *Lariba Wilson Pakmoni, University at Buffalo - SUNY*
- Systems Thinking Through Multi-Sector Climate Literacy

Partnerships. *Shaghig Chaparian, New York University*
Preservice Teacher Education and the Importance of Raising
Awareness of Environmental and Climate Justice. *Leah*
Master, New York University

Chair: *Hailiang Yang, East China Normal University*
Discussant: *Cecilia D Craig, Independent Researcher*

**69.054-10. Early Childhood, Home Language, and Refugee
Family Supports in AANHPI communities (Table 10).**
SIG-Asian Americans and Pacific Islanders in Education and
Research; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 7:45-
9:15am

Participants:

Ethnic Belonging and Racialized Concerns: Karen (Ka-REN)
Immigrant and Refugee Families and School Choice. *Insil*
Jeon, University of Minnesota

Exploration of English literacy readiness among Korean
immigrant families with pre-K children. *Sunyoung Kim,*
University of Illinois at Chicago; So Yeon Kim, Purdue
University; Casey (Keunhee) Kim, University of Hawaii -
Manoa; Jeongae Kang, Illinois State University; Namhee
Kim, University of Illinois at Chicago; Sung-ae Kim, Seoul
National University

Not Just Surviving School: A Community Program as a Third
Space for Burmese Refugee Families. *Jue Wang, University*
of North Carolina - Charlotte; Lan Quach Kolano,
University of North Carolina - Charlotte

Chair: *Mohit P. Mehta, Texas State University*

69.055. AERA Roundtable Session Saturday 7:45 am - Gold 1;
Roundtable Session

**69.055-1. Higher Education Governance and Leadership in
Contested Times (Table 1).** Division J - Postsecondary
Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Strategic Planning in Modern Higher Education: Bridging Gaps
through New Instruments and Insights. *Christopher Adrian*
Thomas, San Diego State University

Culture as Strategy: How Community College Leaders Depict
the Institutional Conditions for Innovation. *Julius Fleschner,*
Georgia Highlands College; Michael Lanford, University of
North Georgia

In the Aftermath: Institutional Support as a Moderator of
Faculty & Staff Mental Health After Hurricane Helene. *R.*
Jason Lynch, Appalachian State University; Chauntee Thrill,
Appalachian State University; Ashley J. Carpenter,
Appalachian State University; Stacey D Garrett,
Appalachian State University; Candice Peters, Appalachian
State University

Predicting the First Black Presidents in U.S. Historically White

Institutions, 1980–2018. *Hannah K. D'Apice, Stanford*
University; Christine Min Wotipka, Stanford University
Senior Leadership Teams and Team Leadership in Colleges of
Education: A Descriptive Analysis. *Kurt S. Sudbrink,*
University of Maryland

69.055-2. Division J Section 6: Roundtable 4 (Table 2), Division
J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Manifesto for Decarbonizing Scholarship and Research: A
Political and Pedagogical Intervention. *Michelle Jordan,*
Arizona State University; Carrie Karsgaard, Cape Breton
University; Andrea E. Weinberg, Arizona State University;
Iveta Silova, Arizona State University; Victoria Desimoni,
Arizona State University; Sandra Nabulega, Arizona State
University

Operationalizing Public Scholarship: Empirical Approaches to
Reimagining Academic Engagement. *Mary K. Littlepage,*
University of Kentucky; Kelly D. Bradley, Marshall
University

Temporal Transformation of Dead and Dying Colleges: From
Funerals to Rising Phoenix. *Ryan M. Allen, Soka University*
of America

Speaking the Unspeakable: Emotional Labor and the Struggle
for Equity in Assessment. *Yi-Chin Wu, Georgia Institute of*
Technology; Mary K. Thompson, University of Wisconsin -
Madison; Beth Janetski, University of Wisconsin - Madison

69.055-3. Designing In-Service PD for STEM Teachers (Table
3). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education;
Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

An Evaluation of The Math for All Professional Learning
Program: A report on teacher Outcomes. *Babette Moeller,*
Education Development Center, Inc.; John H. Hitchcock,
Westat; Jason Schoeneberger, ICF International; Teresa
Garcia Duncan, Deacon Hill Research Associates LLC

In Their Hands: Multimodal Learning Analytics as Reflective-
practice Resources Empowering Mathematics Teachers'
Professional Development. *Alik Palatnik, Hebrew University*
of Jerusalem; Catalina Lomos, Luxembourg Institute of
Socio – Economic Research; Dor Abrahamson, University of
California - Berkeley

Reimagining Equity in Science Education Professional
Development Programs. *Ufomanefe Shola Kayode, Texas*
Tech University; Ali Ahmed, Texas Tech University; Isiaka
Ayobi Raheem, Texas Tech University; Halkano Michael
Hargura, Texas Tech University

The Impact of Workshops and Graduate Coursework on
Mechatronics on STEM Teachers' Efficacy and Beliefs.

Ruthmae Sears, University of South Florida; Stephanie A. Arthur, University of South Florida; Alfredo Rodriguez Vera, University of South Florida; Robert Potter, University of South Florida; Kelley Schuler, University of South Florida; Aizhan Bakytbek, University of South Florida; Alexandro Castellanos, University of South Florida; Brandy Jackson, Aecern

What Enables Integrated STEM? Rethinking Readiness for Transdisciplinary Teaching and Learning. *Jessica Yusaitis Pike, Teachers College, Columbia University; Yingxin Ye, Teachers College, Columbia University; Caron M. Mineo, Teachers College, Columbia University; Madalina Ciocanu, Teachers College, Columbia University; Bryan Keller, Teachers College, Columbia University; Ellen B. Meier, Teachers College, Columbia University*

69.055-4. Innovating STEM: Teacher Resilience, Creativity, and Digital Practice (Table 4). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Exploring Teacher Perceptions of Generative Design Questions in Elementary Mathematics Instruction. *Kolawole Kushimo, University of Massachusetts - Dartmouth; Walter M. Stroup, University of Massachusetts - Dartmouth*

Middle School Science Teachers' Views on Scripted Curriculum in Linguistically Diverse Classrooms. *Sissy S. Wong, University of Houston; Samuel Katende, University of Houston; Maria Alexandra Walsh, University of Houston; Raju Ahmmed, University of Houston; Jie Zhang, University of Houston*

The Effectiveness of an Online Epistemic Game on Professional Teacher Identity Development. *Nur Cakir, Middle East Technical University; Hürriyet Sarıdemir, Middle East Technical University; Neslihan Gök Ayyıldız, Middle East Technical University; Aroutis N. Foster, Drexel University; Diler Oner, Bogazici University*

Chair: *Kolawole Kushimo, University of Massachusetts - Dartmouth*

69.055-5. Critical Perspectives on Policy and Inclusion (Table 5). SIG-Multicultural/Multiethnic Education: Theory, Research and Practice; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

A Case for Culturally Relevant Pedagogy in Developmental English Classrooms at Hispanic-Serving Community Colleges. *Delaney Rood, Michigan State University; Adrienne Hill, Michigan State University*

Cultivating Criticality: Teacher Intentions, Student Experiences, and Possibilities for Futuristic Impact. *Brandi N. Hinnant-Crawford, Clemson University; Emily E. Virtue,*

Western Carolina University; Liz Bergeron, New Tech Network; Morohunkeji Y Orija, Clemson University
Exploring Language and Deculturalization of Native Americans in Teacher Preparation. *Andrew Habana Hafner, Westfield State University*

Using Helm's White Racial Identity Development Model (WRIDM) to Empower Culturally Responsive and Sustaining Preservice Teachers. *Kristina M. Valtierra, Colorado College*

69.055-6. Supporting and Thinking About All Students (Table 6). SIG-Multicultural/Multiethnic Education: Theory, Research and Practice; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Can ChatGPT Help International Students Integrate Socially and Academically in U.S. Universities? A Case Study. *Hasan Aydin, Florida Gulf Coast University; Clarisse Halpern, Florida Gulf Coast University*

Navigating Value Education in Multicultural Societies: Insights from Isaiah Berlin's Theory of Value Pluralism. *Xuan Tang, The University of Sydney; Tian Fu, Capital Normal University*

Tracing Scientific Cultures as Social Epistemologies in Multi-/Intercultural Educational Research through Citation Practices. *Barbara Gross, Free University of Bozen-Bolzano; Edwin Keiner, Goethe-Universität Frankfurt am Main*

Chair: *Arpita Sarker, University of Iowa*

69.055-7. Speaking, Teaching, and Listening to the Truth (Table 7). SIG-Social Studies Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Commitment Issues: Ideological Clarity, Pedagogical Content Knowledge, and the Necessity of Critical Commitment. *Mathew Baker, Georgia Southern University; Cynthia S. Salinas, University of Texas at Austin; Kevin R. Magill, Baylor University*

Cultivating Justice: Curriculum Features That Support K-2 Learners' Justice-Oriented Argumentation in Social Studies. *Ryan E. Hughes, University of North Carolina - Greensboro; Beth Meyer, The Experiential School of Greensboro*

Identity in the Making: Oral History and Teacher Learning in the Teaching of Difficult Histories. *Yonghee Suh, Old Dominion University; Brian J. Daugherty, Virginia Commonwealth University; Joanna K. Garner, Old Dominion University*

"Telling Stories of the People Who Lived Them": Teachers' Classroom Implementation of Historic Site-Based PD. *Rachael E. Rudis, Michigan State University*

The familial curricula of current events. *Nancy Ku Bradt,*

Queens College

69.056. AERA Roundtable Session Saturday 7:45 am - Gold 2;
Roundtable Session

69.056-1. Critical, Inclusive, and Socially Just Perspectives on Higher Education (Table 1). Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Lifting While Climbing: A Narrative of Resilience and Caring Relationships in Higher Education. *Linda Ruiz, California State Polytechnic University - Pomona*

Inclusion as Movement within a Zone of Contestation: Critiquing Static Notions of Inclusion. *Andres A. Arrazola, Florida International University*

Integrating Social Network Analysis with Asset-Based Higher Education Research. *Nidia Bañuelos, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Kyoungjin Jang-Tucci, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Ross J. Benbow, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Paris D. Wicker, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

“Mi Hija, La Independiente”: Latina Mothers and their Commitment toward Independencia for their Daughters. *Leslie Patricia Luqueño, Stanford University*

Chair: *La Quirshia Fennell, Claremont Graduate University*

69.056-2. Data, Accountability, and Political Contexts in Education Finance (Table 2). SIG-Fiscal Issues, Policy and Education Finance; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Building FAIR School Finance Data Systems: A Multi-State and Federal Analysis. *Sarah Volk, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Christopher Saldaña, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Laura Davalos, Wisconsin Center for Education Research; Xinyu Guan, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Ariadna Guerrero, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Brooke Fousek, University of Texas at Austin; Ghipsel Cibrian, Teachers College, Columbia University; Aaron Mathew, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Evaluating Preferences for Private School Choice: Insights from a Conjoint Experiment. *Sara Booher, Grinnell College; Paul Hutchison, Grinnell College; Andreas Jozwiak, Grinnell College*

Policing Milwaukee Public Schools: State Pressure, Legislative Battles, and the Fight Over School Resource Officers. *Gabbi Gruver, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Chair: *Lena Batt, University of Kansas*

69.056-3. Negotiating Ideologies and Constraints in Language

and Literacy Education (Table 3). SIG-Language and Social Processes; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

“Dawning of an Aspect”: Creating Contexts for Articulating Educators’ Changes in Ideological Perspectives on Language. *Kate T. Anderson, Arizona State University; Chris K. Chang-Bacon, University of Virginia; Ashley Yung Batchelor, Arizona State University*

Restrictive Circulations: Global Flows of Narrow Literacy Discourses and Instructional Practices. *Catherine F. Compton-Lilly, University of South Carolina; Carolyn Clarke, St. Francis Xavier University; Kerryn Dixon, University of Nottingham; Annette Woods, Queensland University of Technology*

Chair: *Kate T. Anderson, Arizona State University*

69.056-4. International Explorations of Women in Academia and Teaching (Table 4). SIG-Research on Women and Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Gendered Academic Trajectories in Chilean Higher Education: Doctoral Training, Career Development, and Job Satisfaction. *Pamela Guzmán, Universidad de La Frontera; Daniela Véliz Calderón, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile; Paulina Berríos, Universidad de Chile; Johana Andrea Fuentes, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile*

How Rural Female Teachers’ Leadership Affects their Professional Development? The Chain Mediating Role of Teacher Collaboration and Teacher Self-Efficacy. *Songli Wang, Shandong Women’ University*

Iranian Women’s conditions: A Journey Before, During, and After the Islamic Revolution. *Vajiheh Shahsavari, Kansas State University*

On-Call Mulan: A Qualitative Study on Novice Female Secondary School Teachers’ Embodied Experiences in China. *Jinwen Qu, East China Normal University*

69.056-5. Under Pressure: Teacher Stress, Workload, and the Hidden Cost of the Professions (Table 5). SIG-Stress, Coping, and Resilience; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

A Cross-national Examination of Relationships between Teachers’ Subjective Well-Being, Workload, Stress, and Job Satisfaction. *Tuncer Fidan, Alanya Alaaddin Keykubat University; Turker Kurt, Gazi University; Ahmet Sahin, Alanya Alaaddin Keykubat University; Sinem Arslan Donmez, Alanya Hamdullah Emin Paşa University; Ibrahim Duyar, Arkansas State University*

Assessing Teacher Intentions to Leave Education using the Plans to Leave Current Job Measure. *Richard G. Lambert, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Kristen C. Mosley, University of Texas at Austin; Christopher J. McCarthy, University of Texas at Austin; Alessandra Caldwell, University of North Carolina - Charlotte*

Associations between Working Conditions, Self-Efficacy, and Hair Cortisol Concentration in Preschool Teachers. *Cynthia Arraya Wiltshire, University of Texas - El Paso; Emily C. Merz, Colorado State University; Amanda M. Dettmer, Yale University*

The Unseen Costs of Digital Reform: A Physiological Study of Teacher Stress. *Yuna Oh, Seoul National University; youngsun choo, Seoul National University; Young Hoan Cho, Seoul National University*

Chair: *Richard G. Lambert, University of North Carolina - Charlotte*

69.056-6. Education through an international context (Table 6). SIG-International Studies; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Making sense of data-use policy in high schools in Chile: Good intentions, weak implementation. *Felipe Aravena, Pontificia Universidad Catolica de Valparaiso; Carmen Montecinos, Universidad Catolica de Valparaiso; Bárbara Zoro, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Valparaiso; Monica Cortez, Pontificia Universidad Catolica de Valparaiso; Fabian Campos, Pontificia Universidad Catolica de Valparaiso; Macarena González-Murgas, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Valparaiso; Rebecca Ipinza, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Valparaiso; Belen Barria, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Valparaiso*

Means or Ends? Pedagogical Intentionality and the Politics of Technology Integration in Brazilian Public Education. *Bruna Damiana Heinsfeld, University of Minnesota*

Participatory Approaches to Student Reflection in Short-term, Faculty Led Study Abroad Programs. *Angela L. Eckhoff, Old Dominion University; Jamie Colwell, Old Dominion University*

Systematic Review on International Students' Belonging in U.S. Higher Education. *Eun Jung "EJ" Paik, Pennsylvania State University; Amanda R. Corso, George Mason University; Hanna Kim, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Chair: *Lilian Linialy Chimuma, Colorado Department of Public Health and Environment*

69.056-7. What it All Means: AI and Technology in Education (Table 7). SIG-International Studies; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Cultural Bias in Generative AI's Academic Motivation and Mindset Responses. *Xuming Li, Tsinghua University; Xiaomeng Xu, Tsinghua University; Yu Zhang, Tsinghua University*

Exploring Factors Influencing Turkish Adolescents' Digital Reading Achievement. *Ibrahim Kizil, Syracuse University; Hanifi Yumusak, Turkish Ministry of National Education; Canan Senturk-Barisik, Turkish Ministry of National Education; Secil Kilic, Erciyes University; Fatima Seyma Kizil, Syracuse University*

Introducing Computer Science in Early Childhood Classrooms: Evidence from a Randomized Study in Uruguay. *Deborah ZAK, Ceibal; Francisca Carocca P., Boston College; Camila Porto, Ceibal; Valentina Cancea, Ceibal; javier valente, ceibal; Victor Koleszar, Ceibal*

Chair: *Sabahet S. Bruncaj, United Arab Emirates University*

69.056-8. Educational Ethics (Table 8). SIG-Philosophical Studies in Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Awakening a Consciousness of Possibilities – Defamiliarizing the Present to Imagine Alternative Futures. *Maja Morsing, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Beyond Rational Autonomy as an Educational Aim. *Justin Hauver, Harvard University*

From Hope Punk to Hopeful: Reclaiming Education as a Basic Good in the Face of Neoliberal Instrumentalisation. *Sean Chen Liu, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University*

“Safe to practice and ready to learn”: Toward pedagogically response-able teacher education. *Kyle Kopsick, University of Colorado - Boulder; Barbara S. Stengel, Vanderbilt University*

Situationist Threats in the Classroom: Prospects for Fostering Moral Agency. *Sheron A. Fraser-Burgess, Ball State University*

Chair: *Sean Chen Liu, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University*

69.056-9. An International View of Social Emotional Learning (Table 9). SIG-Social and Emotional Learning; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Exploring Association Between School Climate and Student Social-Emotional Skills in Chinese Cultural and Educational Context. *Jinpeng Niu, Southwest University*

From Discipline to Disengagement: Obesity, Symbolic Stigma, and Socio-Emotional Inequality in Schooling. *yunyi luo, East China Normal University; Jiaqi He, Nanjing University*

Participating in Extracurricular Activities is Associated with

Enhanced Social-Emotional Skills: A Cross-Cultural Investigation. *Yat Mei Suen, Wellesley College; Zixuan Lin, University College London - IOE; Gwyneth Leung, University of California - Los Angeles*

The Relationship Between School Quality and Social-emotional Skills - Evidence from Cambodia. *Bismah Tahir, Vanderbilt University*

Exploring Cross-National Differences in the Mediating Role of Social-Emotional Competence Between Bullying Victimization and Well-Being. *Xuan Wang, University of Hong Kong; Juyeon Lee, The University of Hong Kong*

Chair: *Vanessa Hammler Kenon, University of Texas - San Antonio*

69.057. AERA Roundtable Session Saturday 7:45 am - Gold 3;
Roundtable Session

69.057-1. Examining Social Emotional Development in Early Childhood and through Parenting (Table 1). SIG-Social and Emotional Learning; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Examining Safety Concerns in Early Childhood Education: Implications for Children's Socio-Emotional Well-being. *Isaac Awortwe, University of Texas at Austin; Dandan Liang, University of Houston; Xin Li, University of Houston; Habibah Nabuuma, University of Houston*

Exploring Time Perspective and Social Emotional Learning With Two Early Childhood Teachers. *Ike Bayazitli, University of California - Berkeley; Alison K. Munzer, University of California - Los Angeles; Jabari Mahiri, University of California - Berkeley*

It's Time to Listen: Exploring Historically Marginalized Caregivers' Perception of Social-Emotional Learning. *Kai Zhuang Shum, University of Tennessee; Courteney Johnson, Fordham University; Danbi Choe, Louisiana State University; Sara Castro-Olivo, Texas A&M University*

Maternal and Paternal Parenting Styles and Children's Socio-Emotional Skills: An East-West Comparison. *Qian Nie, East China Normal University; Shiqing Liu, East China Normal University*

Chair: *samia javed, University of Western Ontario*

69.057-2. Learning With and Learning About Each Other (Table 2). SIG-Social Studies Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

A Critical Geographical Approach to Understanding Students' Perspectives of Indigenous History. *Yubing Liu, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Between maintaining teacher impartiality and protecting student dignity: Teachers' responses to unacceptable student

speech about politically sensitive issues in France and Quebec. *Baptiste Roucau, University of Quebec at Trois-Rivières; Bruce Maxwell, Université de Montréal*

(Re)Imagining Civic Education: A Qualitative Phenomenological Study on How Youth Soccer Coaches Cultivate Civic Values in Young Players. *Saviour A. Kitcher, Michigan State University*

Secondary students' dialectical reasoning skills demonstrated in lightly scaffolded essay. *Jada Kohlmeier, Auburn University; Megan Andrews, Auburn University; Sarah I. Bailey, Opelika City Schools; David T. Marshall, Auburn University*

69.057-3. AI supported writing: Tracing engagement and learning (Table 3). SIG-Advanced Technologies for Learning; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

An umbrella review on conversational AI in language learning (CoALL). *Weijiao Huang, University of Hong Kong; Xinyuan Yang, University of Hong Kong; Luke K. Fryer, University of Hong Kong*

Artificial Intelligence for Learning Engagement: A Meta-Analysis. *Shuchen Guo, Nanjing Normal University; Lehong Shi, University of Georgia; Xiaoming Zhai, University of Georgia*

Beyond the Score: Demographic Influence on AI Justifications in Writing Assessment. *Ghaida S. Alrawashdeh, Oakland University*

Exploring the Use of LLMs for Assessing Creativity in Student Programming Artifacts. *Zifeng Liu, University of Florida; Wanli Xing, University of Florida*

Tracing EFL Learners' Emotional Journeys in Human-AI Collaborative Writing: A Control-Value Perspective Multiple Case Study. *Shujun YUAN, University of Sydney; YUNAN ZHANG, University of Hong Kong*

Chair: *Nicole Marie DelMastro-Jeffery, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

69.057-4. Human-AI Partnerships, Ethics, and Reflective Practice (Table 4). SIG-Design and Technology; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Dialogues with the Machine: Human-AI Feedback Loops in Human-Centered Design. *Akash Kumar Saini, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Saadeddine S. Shehab, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; William Cope, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Mary Kalantzis, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Duane Searsmith, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Vania Castro, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Champaign; Amber Dewey Schultz, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign

How Professional Experience Shapes Reflection in a MOOC on Generative AI and Learning Experience Design. *Rebecca M. Quintana, University of Michigan; Chris Quintana, University of Michigan; Yuanru Tan, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Joy Hong, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Knowledge, Critique, and Practice: A Conceptual Model for Understanding and Designing Pre-Service Teachers' AI Training. *Mazid Ul Hasan, University of Cincinnati*

Chair: *Md Mamunur Rashid, University of Rochester*

Discussant: *Wisdom Yao Nudze, Texas A&M University*

69.057-5. Examining Evaluation Toward More Inclusive Informal Learning Environments (Table 5). SIG- Informal Learning Environment Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Applying an Intersectional Lens to Evaluate Informal STEM Education Programs with Health and Medical Themes. *Ting Dai, University of Illinois at Chicago; Yuxuan Zhi, Alameda County Office of Education*

Ecologically Validating the Science Curiosity SCILE Scale in a STEM-Making Summer Camp. *Jennifer L. Weible, Central Michigan University; Heather Toomey Zimmerman, Pennsylvania State University; Gabriela T. Richard, University of Massachusetts - Amherst*

Exploring the Practice-Theory Relationship in Museum Evaluation. *Kari Ross Nelson, Utah State University; Lisa Lundgren, Utah State University*

Harvesting Diverse Methodologies to Tell a Holistic Story of Early Learning in Museums. *Nicole Cromartie, University of Colorado - Denver; Lori Geismar Ryan, University of Colorado - Denver*

69.057-6. Engaging in Arts and Making as Acts of Transformative Identity Building (Table 6). SIG-Learning Sciences; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Artmaking as Assertion: Youth Artmaking as Cultural Learning Pathways Toward New Identities. *Kristina M. Stamatis, University of Nebraska Omaha; Joseph L. Polman, University of Colorado - Boulder; Marisa Mendoza-Maurer, University of Colorado - Boulder; Tania Hogan, University of Colorado - Boulder*

Joyful Immigrant Family Storytelling During Politically Perilous Times. *Antero Garcia, Stanford University; Alix Dick, La Cuenta*

Educator Learning and Mutual Becoming in a STEAM and Storytelling Program. *Teyona James-Harris, Northwestern*

University; Shirin Vossoughi, Northwestern University; Lulu Madise, McGaw YMCA

“We Are All Becoming”: Exploring the Design of Improvisational Activity within Researcher-Artist Collaborations. *Ananda M. Marin, University of California - Los Angeles; Trinity Collins, University of California - Los Angeles; Shivani Dave, University of California - Los Angeles; Lindsay Lindberg, University of California - Los Angeles*

Chair: *Aachey Susan Jurow, University of Colorado - Boulder*

69.057-7. Educational Trauma and Health Equity: Building Bridges Between Public Health and Education (Table 7). Division I - Education in the Professions; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Our Bodies Remember: Educational Trauma, Microaggressions, Micro-Affirmations, and the Weathering of Black Girls. *Sonya Lynette Brooks, University of California, Los Angeles; Passion Faith Lord, University of California - Los Angeles*

Youth of Today: The Unequal Starting Line (An Interactive Activity on Youth Depression Risk). *Jessica Jaiyeola, Claremont Graduate University; Angelica Bradley, University of California - Los Angeles*

Abolitionist Health Justice: Reimagining Educational Policy through a Public Health Lens. *Patricia Ordoñez-Kim, University of California - Riverside*

Chair: *Courtney Thomas Tobin, University of California - Los Angeles*

Discussant: *Kia Skrine Jeffers, University of California - Los Angeles*

69.057-8. Active Learning and Technology Integration in Preservice Education: Developing Competencies for Future Classrooms (Table 8). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

GAI-Enhanced Courses: Examining the Impact on Pre-Service Science Teachers' TPACK Development. *Xiaomei Yan, Shanghai Jiao Tong University*

Getting Active! Teacher Candidates' Perceptions of Active learning Tasks and Classroom Design on Their Practice. *Cathy Marks Krpan, University of Toronto - OISE; Sonya Ho, University of Toronto - OISE*

Investigating the Integration of Computational Thinking into Mathematics through Pre-Service Math Teachers' Instructional Designs. *Rumeysa Beyazhancer, Bursa Uludag University; Barış Demir, Kocaeli University*

Chair: *Julie Johnson, The Ohio State University*

69.058. AERA Roundtable Session Saturday 7:45 am - Gold 4;
Roundtable Session

69.058-1. Co-Constructing Knowledge between Research and School Practice: Qualitative Approaches in Two German Research Projects (Table 1). Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Participatory Social Network Analysis: Methodological Reflections on Co-constructive Knowledge Production in Multi-professional School Networks. *Mirjam Maier-Roeseler, University of Education Karlsruhe; Mariella A. Winter, Pädagogische Hochschule Karlsruhe*

Focus Groups as Sites for Reflection and Dialogue between Research, Practice, and Educational Administration. *Anne Bödicker, Pädagogische Hochschule Karlsruhe; Gabriele Maria Weigand, University of Education Karlsruhe*

Meta-Reflection as a Strategy for Research and Professionalization in the Collaboration between Research and Practice. *Corinna Maulbetsch, University of Education - Heidelberg; Mirjam Maier-Roeseler, University of Education Karlsruhe*

Chair: *Gabriele Maria Weigand, University of Education Karlsruhe*

Discussants: *Christian Fischer, University of Münster; Miriam Vock, University of Potsdam*

69.058-2. Structural Forces and Storywork: Qualitative Methodologies for Understanding Identity, Inequity, and Opportunity (Table 2). Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

A Phenomenological Exploration of International Students' Barriers to Employment in China. *Jiaqi Tang, Tsinghua University*

Critical Race Theory and Cultural Historical Activity Theory in education: Surfacing and disrupting systemic inequities. *Doron Zinger, California State University - Dominguez Hills; Socorro Cambero, University of California - Irvine; Abdul-Rehman M. Issa, University of California - San Diego*

Cultural Profiles as Narrative Methodology for STEM Identity of Emerging Island-Based Scientist. *Rodney K. Hopson, American University; Manuel A. Pérez-Troncoso, PUCV-CIAE Postdoctoral Researcher; Cecilia Noelle Vaughn-Guy, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Chair: *Jiaqi Tang, Tsinghua University*

69.058-3. Exploring Identity Formation: Underrepresented

Learners' Experiences in the Professions (Table 3).

Division I - Education in the Professions; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Exploring Pre-Medical Experiences of First-Generation Medical Students. *Devasmita Chakraverty, Indian Institute of Management; Branden Eggan, Albany Medical College, Union College, Siena College; Hyacinth R.C. Mason, Tufts University; Hannah L'Etoile, Brown University; Jacqueline Diaz, Tufts University; Valerie Rivera, Siena College; Brandon Ascencio, Albany Medical College; Catie Havemann, University of North Carolina, Dept of Emergency Medicine; Regina G. Russell, Vanderbilt University; Tasha R. Wyatt, Uniformed Services University of the Health Sciences; Dowin H. Boatright, New York University; Mytien Nguyen, Yale University*

Gals and Pals in Engineering: A First-Year Learning Community's Impact on Women's Engineering Identity. *David J Melnichuk, University of California - Davis; Angelika Aldea Tamura, University of California - Davis; Tiffany Marie Chan, University of California - Davis; Ahwa Melodie Razavian, University of California - Davis; Carrissah Calvin, University of California - Davis; Xianglong Wang, University of California - Davis*

The Art of Becoming: Professional Identity Formation of Black Women in Medicine and Pharmacy. *Ashley M. Leach, University of Southern California*

Understanding how Medical Students Make Meaning of their Rural First-Generation Identity and Medical School Experiences Using an Ecological Systems Framework. *Devasmita Chakraverty, Indian Institute of Management; Catie Havemann, University of North Carolina, Dept of Emergency Medicine; Hannah L'Etoile, Brown University; Lala Forrest, Yale University; Brianna De Oliveira, Tufts University; Nicole O'Neal, New England Board of Higher Education; Hyacinth R.C. Mason, Tufts University; Mytien Nguyen, Yale University; Tasha R. Wyatt, Uniformed Services University of the Health Sciences; Dowin H. Boatright, New York University*

Chair: *Mary Roduta Roberts, University of Alberta*

69.058-4. Leading with Ethical Commitments in Research Design (Table 4). SIG-Qualitative Research; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Confessions of a Bureaucratic Cynic Reimagining Ethics Education Through IRB Practice in Qualitative Research. *Jonathan M. Coker, Coastal Carolina University*

Portraiture Across Platforms and Places: Methodological Possibilities From Multi-sited Literacy Research. *Maggie*

Bryant, Baylor University; Carlson Coogler, Baylor University; Tony Lee Talbert, Baylor University
Visualizing Belonging: Reflections on Photo Elicitation in a Phenomenological Study of Belonging. *Kathryn Polley, University of Georgia*
Chair: *Kristen Schaffer, Mount Royal University*

69.058-5. Admissions in Focus: Equity, Predictive Insights, and Holistic Review (Table 5). Division I - Education in the Professions; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Applicant Factors and Residency Performance: A Meta Analysis with Implications for Holistic Review. *Nathan Kuncel, University of Minnesota; Monica M. Cuddy, NBME; Isaac M Bazian,, University of Minnesota; Michael Hazboun, University of Minnesota; Ming Him Tai, Pennsylvania State University; Christopher Feddock, National Board of Medical Examiners*

Data-Driven Insights: Predicting Foundations-Level Success and Step 1 Completion in Active Learning Curriculum. *Yichen Zhao, University of Vermont; Karen Lounsbury, University of Vermont; Kathryn N. Huggett, University of Vermont; Leila Amiri, University of Vermont*

The Use of Artificial Intelligence in Medical School Admissions: Can We Be Fair and Efficient? *Leila Amiri, University of Vermont; Ioannis Koutroulis, George Washington University; Alexander MacIntosh, Altus Assessments*

Where Applicants Graduate Matters: Understanding Individual Attributes and College Characteristics in Texas Medical Admissions. *Shirley Yang Anderson, University of North Texas; Hyun Kyoung Ro, Korea University*

Chair: *Amanda K. Burbage, Old Dominion University*

69.058-6. Unforgetting, Worldmaking, Navigating, and Creating: Literacies of Teacher Education (Table 6). SIG-Writing and Literacies; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Unforgetting Histories in Writing Teacher Preparation: Preservice Teachers' Multimodal Compositions as Windows to Resisting Assimilation. *Kristen Driscoll, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Erica Holyoke, University of Colorado - Denver; Susan Tily, University of Wisconsin - Eau Claire*

Writing as Worldmaking: Digital Pen-Pal Partnership in Teacher Education for Reclaiming Voice, Joy, and Possibility. *Erica Holyoke, University of Colorado - Denver; Susan Tily, University of Wisconsin - Eau Claire*

"All These Ways to Slyly Maneuver": Navigating Niceness During Student Teaching. *Christopher Kingsland, Towson*

University

Designing a Mentoring Environment to Support Prospective Teacher Learning about Writing, Writers, and Writing Instruction. *Sarah W. Beck, New York University; Kate Lan, New York University; Michelle Hu, New York University*
Chair: *Molly C. Marek, University of Texas at Austin*

Division and SIG Posters

69.059. AERA Poster Session Saturday 7:45 am; Poster Session

69.059-1. Modes and Mechanisms for Enacting Teacher Agency, Activism, and Leadership. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 7:45-9:15am

Posters:

1. Early career teachers' professional agency in the professional community and working environment fit (Poster 1). *Liyuan E, University of Helsinki; Jenni Sullanmaa, University of Helsinki; Auli Toom, University of Helsinki; Kirsi Maria Pyhalto, University of Helsinki*
2. Teacher Agency: A Thematic and Poetic Inquiry into Teacher Reflections on Generative AI in Education (Poster 2). *Angelie Ignacio, University of Toronto - OISE; Eunice Eunhee Jang, University of Toronto - OISE*
3. Enacting Language Teacher Agency in Digital Technology Use through Collaborative Inquiry (Poster 3). *Kyu Yun Lim, University of British Columbia*
4. "What About My Kids?" Teachers Navigating Tensions Between Linguistically Responsive PD And CCR Curriculum (Poster 4). *Caryn M. Calisi, University of Texas at San Antonio; Jerry Romero, University of Texas - San Antonio; Bedrettin Yazan, University of Texas - San Antonio; Jorge L. Solis, University of Texas - San Antonio; Kristen Lindahl, University of Texas - San Antonio; MICHAEL MAURICIO, University of Texas - San Antonio*
5. The Impact Mechanism of Master Teacher Leadership on the Master Teacher Studios Effectiveness in China (Poster 5). *Chenyu Cao, East China Normal University; Feiye Wang, East China Normal University; Yutong Wu, East China Normal University*

69.059-2. Developing PreK-12 Teachers for Culturally Responsive Practice: A Review of Interventions and Quantitative Measures. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 7:45-9:15am

Poster:

6. Developing PreK-12 Teachers for Culturally Responsive Practice: A Review of Interventions and Quantitative Measures (Poster 6). *I-Chun Hsiao, University of Iowa;*

Qianyi Gao, University of Iowa

69.059-3. Justice, Ethics, and Innovation in Teacher Education: Feedback Loops, Computational Thinking, and Comparative Perspectives. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 7:45-9:15am

Posters:

7. From Analytical Programs to Standards: Mapping Panamanian Teacher Education Curricula with Chilean Pedagogical Standards (Poster 7). *Mariana Leon, Quality Leadership University & CIEDU; Nadia De León, Centro de Investigación Educativa AIP; Maria Alejandra Quintero, Quality Leadership University, CIEDU AIP; Maria Beatriz Fernandez Cofre, Universidad de Chile; Carmen Montecinos, Universidad Católica de Valparaíso; Elias De Leon, University of Panama; Ricardo Acosta, University of Panama; Laura Villarreal, Quality Leadership University; Luz Caballero, University of Panama*
8. Integrating Computational Thinking across Elementary Subjects (Poster 8). *Shenghua Zha, University of South Alabama; Lauren Brannan, Alabama State Department of Education; Na Gong, University of South Alabama; Sanju Gharti Chhetri G C, University of South Alabama; Kelly O. Byrd, University of South Alabama; Drew Gossen, University of South Alabama; Todd Johnson, University of South Alabama; Jennifer Simpson, University of South Alabama; Karen Morrison, University of South Alabama*
9. In the Absence of the School Leader: How Administrative Visibility Shapes Student-Teacher Perceptions (Poster 9). *Angus Shiva Mungal, University of Mississippi; Dennis A. Bunch, University of Mississippi*
10. What Works?: Reimagining Pre-service Teacher Education in Rural China with the Simple Interactions Approach (Poster 10). *Amelea Ng, One Village One Preschool Project; Xiaoyue Dai, Harvard University; Xuerong Wang, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Junlei Li, Harvard University; Si Chen, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Catherine E. Snow, Harvard University*
11. Confidence Levels of Future Educators in Working with Individuals with Disabilities (Poster 11). *Adrian Woo Jung, California State University; Sung Hee Lee, California State University - Fullerton*
12. Simulated IEP Meetings for Preservice Teachers: A Systematic Review (Poster 12). *Joelle Fingerhut, Marist College*

69.059-4. Mentoring, Induction, Novice Teacher Support, and Mental Health. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 7:45-9:15am

Posters:

13. A Systematic Review of Novice Perceptions on Mentor Practices (Poster 13). *Riku Sayuj, University of Pennsylvania*
14. “Bonus extra mentor teacher”: Exploring the Fourth Person in a Pre-service Teacher Mentorship Triad (Poster 14). *Melanie F. Hardy-Skeberdis, Penn State University*
15. Bridging Policy Gaps through Re-envisioning Mentorship: Supporting Rural and Remote Early Career Teachers (Poster 15). *Darriya Starr, RTI International; McCaila Ingold-Smith, RTI International; Guillermo Dominguez, RTI International; Cheyane Mitchell, RTI International; Katherine McKnight, RTI International*
16. Productive Collaboration and Dialogue: The Role of Openness to Mutual Shaping through Transaction in Mentoring (Poster 16). *Kristina E. Bell, Virginia Tech*
17. Reimagining Induction: Co-Teaching and Collaborative Action Research as Signature Pedagogies for Professional Relationships and Learning (Poster 17). *Ciara Uí Chonduibh, Scoil Naomh Fiach*
18. Shifting Trends, Strategic Needs: Examining Educator Retention in Pennsylvania by Experience Level and Location-Based Characteristics (Poster 18). *Megan Foley, Pennsylvania Department of Education; Rhonda Johnson, Pennsylvania Department of Education; Candy M. Miller, Lancaster Lebanon IU13*
19. Supporting Beginning Teachers and Principals: A Systemic Approach to a Persistent Challenge (Poster 19). *Ainat Guberman, David Yellin College of Education; Rinat Arviv Elyashiv, Kibbutzim College of Education; Gal Ben-Yehudah, The Open University of Israel*
20. Teachers’ Joys and Stressors: Investigating the Experiences of Novice Teachers (Poster 20). *Annie McClellan, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*
21. The Effect of Mental Health Induction Supports on Teacher Mental Health Outcomes: A Causal Machine Learning Approach (Poster 21). *Amota Ataneka, University of Cincinnati; Benjamin Kelcey, University of Cincinnati; Leigh McLean, University of Delaware; Peter A. Youngs, University of Virginia; Jean Baptiste Habarurema, University of Cincinnati*
22. Three Years In: Reflective Consultation and Trauma-Informed Practice Mitigate Secondary Trauma in Novice Teachers (Poster 22). *Kathryn S. Young, Metropolitan State University of Denver; Ofelia Castro Schepers, Purdue University; Megan Brennan, Resilient Futures*
23. Understanding System Influences on Mentoring Practices for Early Career Teachers (Poster 23). *Beth Maloch, University of Texas at Austin; Melissa Mosley Wetzel, University of Texas at Austin; Emily McDonald, University of Texas at Austin; Valerie Taylor, University of Texas at Austin; Kelsie Corrison Burnett, University of Texas at Austin; Angie House, University of Texas at Austin; LeAnne Leshner Hernandez, University of Texas at Austin; Emily Maurer, University of Texas at Austin; Kelly Ocasio, University of Texas at Austin*
24. What Keeps Them Teaching? Rethinking Induction for

Special Educators Who Stay (Poster 24). *Margaret L. Kamman, University of Florida; Kate Zimmer, Kennesaw State University; Melissa Kypraios Driver, Kennesaw State University; Jocelyn Cooledge, Center Street Consulting*

25. Tailored teacher induction: predicting alignment between changes in motivation and provided induction support (Poster 25). *Xiangyuan Feng, University of Groningen; Michelle Helms-Lorenz, University of Groningen*

69.059-5. From Adoption to Transformation: AI Integration, Critical Pedagogy, and Sustaining Futures in Teacher Preparation. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 7:45-9:15am

Posters:

26. Artificial Intelligence in Teacher Education: A Systematic Scoping Review of Five Years (Poster 26). *Afaq Ahmed, Texas A&M University; Andrew Kwok, Texas A&M University*
27. Beyond AI Adoption: K-12 Teachers' Generative Learning in AI-Integrated Teaching Practice (Poster 27). *chenlu liu, East China Normal University; Zheng Xin, East China Normal University*
28. Exploring Teachers' Integration of Generative AI: A Case Study of Processes and Influencing Factors (Poster 28). *Zicong Song, The University of Hong Kong; Jingjing Qin, University of Hong Kong; Fangzhou Jin, The University of Hong Kong; Wai Ming Cheung, University of Hong Kong; Chin-Hsi Lin, University of Hong Kong*
29. Imagining Culturally and Linguistically Sustaining AI Literacy with In-Service Educators through Design-Based Research (Poster 29). *Kali Peracchia, Denver Public Schools*
30. Integrating AI-Facilitated Technologies in Graduate Education to Support Sustainable, Longitudinal Learning in K-12 Schools (Poster 30). *HeeKap Lee, Azusa Pacific University; Jennifer Courduff, Azusa Pacific University*
31. Is an AI affordance really an affordance? Emergent curriculum tensions during pre-service teacher noticing (Poster 31). *Victoria L. Delaney, San Diego State University; Ryan Gabriel Aniceto, San Diego State University*
32. Reimagining Teacher Education: Critical Pedagogy and Practice in the Age of AI (Poster 32). *Melissa Warr, New Mexico State University; Suparna Chatterjee, New Mexico State University; Nicole Oster, Arizona State University; Sage Peterson, New Mexico State University*
33. Strategic genAI Use in Proving: Effects of Sequence on Student Learning and Reasoning (Poster 33). *Hyunkyoungh Yoon, California State Polytechnic University, Pomona; Yujin Lee, Kangwon National University; Kyungwon Lee, Seoul National University; Oh Nam Kwon, Seoul National University*
34. The dark side of AI in Teacher Education: Evidence from a

Systematic Review (Poster 34). *Hanxue Lv, East China Normal University; Chao Cheng, East China Normal University*

69.059-6. Redefining Violence: Mapping Disciplinary Codes and Racial Disparities in California School Districts. Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 7:45-9:15am

Poster:

35. Redefining Violence: Mapping Disciplinary Codes and Racial Disparities in California School Districts (Poster 35). *Imani Dixon, University of California - Los Angeles*

69.059-7. Orienting to Affect, Culture, and Language in Science Teaching and Learning. SIG-Science Teaching and Learning; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 7:45-9:15am

Posters:

36. Decolonizing STEM Learning Spaces: Contemplative Traditions as the Bedrock of Creativity & Healing (Poster 36). *Raaghav Pandya, City University of New York; Christopher Emdin, Teachers College, Columbia University*
37. Reimagining Science Education Through the 5Cs: A Framework for Futures-Oriented Pedagogy in Secondary Classrooms (Poster 37). *Kristine Lee Callis-Duehl, Donald Danforth Plant Science Center; Ruth Kaggwa, Danforth Plant Science Center; Sandra Arango-Caro, Donald Danforth Plant Science Center*
38. Do Woman Teachers Make Woman Scientists?: Gender Matching, Science Identity, and STEM College Major Intent (Poster 38). *Raymond Jacobs-Edmondson, Claremont Graduate University; Guan Saw, Claremont Graduate University*
39. From the Soil to the Soul: Humanizing Science Education for a Healthier Future (Poster 39). *Miriam M. Ortiz, University of Texas - Rio Grande Valley*
40. Science Teachers' Adoption of Virtual Laboratories in Rural South African Schools: Challenges and Opportunities (Poster 40). *BRIAN SHAMBARE, University of the Free State; Thuthukile Jita, University of the Free State*
41. How are affective factors studied in science education: A critical review on science affective factors (Poster 41). *Xiang HU, Renmin University of China; Siyuan Wang, Renmin University of China; Tao Wang, Renmin University of China*
42. Idiosyncratic Constructed Emotions During Science Documentary Viewing (Poster 42). *Brian W. Miller, Towson University*
43. STEM for community transformation: Centering youth agency and interest in STEM integration (Poster 43). *Khanh Tran, Utah State University; Lynn A. Bryan, Purdue University; Selcen Guzey, Purdue University*

44. Teachers' Beliefs, Preparedness, and Instructional Practices for Teaching NGSS Science With Multilingual Learners (Poster 44). *Abigail Schwenger, New York University; Alison M. Haas, New York University; Scott Grapin, University of Miami; Alycia Sterenberg Mahon, Western Michigan University; Jessaca K. Spybrook, Western Michigan University; Courtney Plumley, Horizon Research, Inc.; Okhee Lee, New York University*
45. Tensions and Affordances of Transformative Pedagogies in a Multilingual Secondary Science Classroom (Poster 45). *Alexis Rutt, James Madison University*
46. Teaching by Hand: Gesture as a Multimodal Tool in Bilingual Science & Math Instruction (Poster 46). *Zenaida Aguirre-Munoz, University of California - Merced; Fernando Negrete Raya, University of California, Merced; Chen Liu, University of California - Merced; Bianca Barajas-Salazar, University of California - Merced*
47. The Messy Joy of Doing Science: Epistemic Affect in Pre-Service Science Teacher Learning (Poster 47). *Elizabeth Finlayson Harris, Stanford University*
48. Unforgetting and Reimagining: Translanguaging for Inclusive Science Futures (Poster 48). *Lourdes Cardozo-Gaibisso, Mississippi State University; Georgia Wood Hodges, University of Georgia*
49. Investigating the Impact of AI-Driven Differentiated Instruction in K-12 Science Classrooms (Poster 49). *Alicia Cotabish, University of Central Arkansas; Deborah D. Dailey, University of Central Arkansas*

69.059-8. Ethics, Epistemology, and Critical Perspectives on AI in Education. SIG-Technology as an Agent of Change in Teaching and Learning; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 7:45-9:15am

Posters:

50. Learning with Machines: Charting the Epistemic Map of Indonesian Students' Perceptions of Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI) (Poster 50). *Ahmad Ardillah Rahman, University College London - IOE; Aziz Awaludin, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Ibrahim -, Monash University*
51. Examining U.S. Parents' Perceptions of the Use of AI in K-12 Education (Poster 51). *Rachel Min Wong, University of Tennessee; Timara McCollum, University of Tennessee; Lynn L. Hodge, University of Tennessee; Catherine Schuman, University of Tennessee*
52. Ethics in AI Education: A Systematic Review of Interventions and Frameworks (Poster 52). *Clelia Perez-Medina, University of Florida; Loraine Cisternas-Garcia, University of Florida; Andrea Ramirez-Salgado, University of Florida; Pasha Antonenko, University of Florida*
53. Towards the Critical Use of AI in Foreign Language Learning: Insights from AI-assisted Songwriting (Poster 53). *Yesul Han, University of Virginia; Yunjeong Chang, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

54. Exploring how middle school students and teachers can thoughtfully and ethically engage with AI technologies (Poster 54). *Christine Wusylko, Kennesaw State University; Xiaoman Wang, Western Michigan University; Bridget Newell, University of Florida; Angela M. Kohnen, University of Florida; Loraine Cisternas-Garcia, University of Florida; Priyadharshini Ganapathy Prasad, University of Florida; Albert Dieter Ritzhaupt, University of Florida; Anthony Botelho, University of Florida; Kevin Cen, University of Florida*

69.059-9. Program Design and Praxis in Preservice Teacher Education: Emotions, Efficacy, and Community Engagement. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 7:45-9:15am

Posters:

55. Effects of Expressive Emotional Writing on Emotional Intelligence and Discourse of Pre-Service Preschool Teachers (Poster 55). *Yu-Ju Chou, National Tsing Hua University*
56. Investigating Pre-Service Teachers' Perceived Program Support and Its Relationship to Teaching Self-Efficacy Across Traditional and Apprenticeship Pathways (Poster 56). *Trenton Dawson, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Burak Sahin, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Amanda Hoffman, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Michael Hack, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Kenneth J. Varner, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*
57. Pre-Service Teachers' Program Satisfaction and Retention: Academic Experience, Professional Commitment, Teaching Efficacy, and Academic Engagement (Poster 57). *Hyun-Joo Jeon, University of Nevada - Reno; Brianna Barnes, University of Nevada - Reno; Jillian Way, University of Nevada - Reno; Ravyn Routsis, University of Nevada - Reno*
58. Reimagining Teacher Preparation through Critical Community Field Experiences for Multilingual Learner Advocacy (Poster 58). *Lucia Cardenas Curiel, Michigan State University; Hye-In Yang, Michigan State University; Ming Ming Cheung, Michigan State University; Yetunde S. Alabede, Michigan State University; Kunti Adhikari, Michigan State University*
59. Teacher Development Through Praxis Experiences: Pre-Service Teachers Navigating Pedagogical Mismatch in Local Schools (Poster 59). *Jennifer L. McCarthy Foubert, North Central College; Mary E. Lyons, Knox College*
60. Validation of a Classroom Assessment Self-Efficacy Scale for Preservice Teachers (Poster 60). *Yiyun Fan, Binghamton University - SUNY; Timothy D. Folger, Binghamton University - SUNY; Connor J. Sondergeld, MetriKs; Toni A. May, Binghamton University - SUNY; Gregory E. Stone, University of Toledo*

Chair: *Sarah D. Lent, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

69.060. e-Lightning Ed-Talk Session 15 - Stage 1. AERA e-Lightning Ed-Talks; AERA Ed Talk
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Exhibit Hall A
- Stage 1; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Teacher Agency: A Thematic and Poetic Inquiry into Teacher Reflections on Generative AI in Education (Stage 1, 7:59 AM). *Angelie Ignacio, University of Toronto - OISE; Eunice Eunhee Jang, University of Toronto - OISE*

Enacting Language Teacher Agency in Digital Technology Use through Collaborative Inquiry (Stage 1, 8:08 AM). *Kyu Yun Lim, University of British Columbia*

“What About My Kids?” Teachers Navigating Tensions Between Linguistically Responsive PD And CCR Curriculum (Stage 1, 8:17 AM). *Caryn M. Calisi, University of Texas at San Antonio; Jerry Romero, University of Texas - San Antonio; Bedrettin Yazan, University of Texas - San Antonio; Jorge L. Solis, University of Texas - San Antonio; Kristen Lindahl, University of Texas - San Antonio; MICHAEL MAURICIO, University of Texas - San Antonio*

Confidence Levels of Future Educators in Working with Individuals with Disabilities (Stage 1, 8:26 AM). *Adrian Woo Jung, California State University; Sung Hee Lee, California State University - Fullerton*

What Works?: Reimagining Pre-service Teacher Education in Rural China with the Simple Interactions Approach (Stage 1, 8:35 AM). *Amelea Ng, One Village One Preschool Project; Xiaoyue Dai, Harvard University; Xuerong Wang, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Junlei Li, Harvard University; Si Chen, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Catherine E. Snow, Harvard University*

In the Absence of the School Leader: How Administrative Visibility Shapes Student-Teacher Perceptions (Stage 1, 8:44 AM). *Angus Shiva Mungal, University of Mississippi; Dennis A. Bunch, University of Mississippi*

Chair: *Katherine Schultz, University of Colorado - Boulder*

69.061. e-Lightning Ed-Talk Session 15 - Stage 2. AERA e-Lightning Ed-Talks; AERA Ed Talk
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Exhibit Hall A
- Stage 2; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Teaching by Hand: Gesture as a Multimodal Tool in Bilingual Science & Math Instruction (Stage 2, 7:50 AM). *Zenaida Aguirre-Munoz, University of California - Merced; Fernando Negrete Raya, University of California, Merced; Chen Liu, University of California - Merced; Bianca Barajas-Salazar, University of California - Merced*

Tensions and Affordances of Transformative Pedagogies in a Multilingual Secondary Science Classroom (Stage 2, 7:59 AM). *Alexis Rutt, James Madison University*

From the Soil to the Soul: Humanizing Science Education for a Healthier Future (Stage 2, 8:08 AM). *Miriam M. Ortiz,*

University of Texas - Rio Grande Valley

Do Woman Teachers Make Woman Scientists?: Gender Matching, Science Identity, and STEM College Major Intent (Stage 2, 8:17 AM). *Raymond Jacobs-Edmondson, Claremont Graduate University; Guan Saw, Claremont Graduate University*

A Systematic Review of Novice Perceptions on Mentor Practices (Stage 2, 8:26 AM). *Riku Sayuj, University of Pennsylvania*

Reimagining Induction: Co-Teaching and Collaborative Action Research as Signature Pedagogies for Professional Relationships and Learning (Stage 2, 8:35 AM). *Ciara Ui Chonduibh, Scoil Naomh Fiach*

Supporting Beginning Teachers and Principals: A Systemic Approach to a Persistent Challenge (Stage 2, 8:44 AM). *Ainat Guberman, David Yellin College of Education; Rinat Arviv Elyashiv, Kibbutzim College of Education; Gal Ben-Yehudah, The Open University of Israel*

Teachers’ Joys and Stressors: Investigating the Experiences of Novice Teachers (Stage 2, 8:53 AM). *Annie McClellan, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Chair: *Kristen Duncan, Clemson University*

69.062. e-Lightning Ed-Talk Session 15 - Stage 3. AERA e-Lightning Ed-Talks; AERA Ed Talk
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Exhibit Hall A
- Stage 3; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Artificial Intelligence in Teacher Education: A Systematic Scoping Review of Five Years (Stage 3, 7:50 AM). *Afaq Ahmed, Texas A&M University; Andrew Kwok, Texas A&M University*

Beyond AI Adoption: K-12 Teachers’ Generative Learning in AI-Integrated Teaching Practice (Stage 3, 7:59 AM). *chenlu liu, East China Normal University; Zheng Xin, East China Normal University*

Imagining Culturally and Linguistically Sustaining AI Literacy with In-Service Educators through Design-Based Research (Stage 3, 8:08 AM). *Kali Peracchia, Denver Public Schools*

Integrating AI-Facilitated Technologies in Graduate Education to Support Sustainable, Longitudinal Learning in K-12 Schools (Stage 3, 8:17 AM). *HeeKap Lee, Azusa Pacific University; Jennifer Courduff, Azusa Pacific University*

Is an AI affordance really an affordance? Emergent curriculum tensions during pre-service teacher noticing (Stage 3, 8:26 AM). *Victoria L. Delaney, San Diego State University; Ryan Gabriel Aniceto, San Diego State University*

Reimagining Teacher Education: Critical Pedagogy and Practice in the Age of AI (Stage 3, 8:35 AM). *Melissa Warr, New Mexico State University; Suparna Chatterjee, New Mexico State University; Nicole Oster, Arizona State University; Sage Peterson, New Mexico State University*

Ethics in AI Education: A Systematic Review of Interventions and Frameworks (Stage 3, 8:44 AM). *Clelia Perez-Medina,*

University of Florida; Loraine Cisternas-Garcia, University of Florida; Andrea Ramirez-Salgado, University of Florida; Pasha Antonenko, University of Florida

Chair: Courtney A. Bell, University of Wisconsin - Madison

Saturday, April 11th, 8:00 am

AERA Sessions

70.010. 2025 Social Justice in Education Award Lecture: Beyond Learned Powerlessness to Educational Liberation. AERA Sessions; Invited Speaker Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 403A;
8:00-9:15am

Chair: Denise M. Taliaferro Baszile, Wayne State University

Presenter: Gloria S. Boutte, University of South Carolina

WERA Sessions

70.011. World Education Research Association Council Executive Committee (Closed). World Education Research Association; Board Meeting
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Studio III - Division Meeting Room; 8:00am to 12:00pm

Chair: Liesel Ebersohn, University of Pretoria

Participants: Bee Leng Chua, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University; Joe O'Hara, Dublin City University; Geovana Mendonça Lunardi Mendes, Universidade do Estado de Santa Catarina; Rocío García-Carrion, University of Deusto; Mustafa Yunus Eryaman, Canakkale Onsekiz Mart University; Felice J. Levine, AERA Emerita; Carine Jonker, World Education Research Association; Gunjana Kuntamarat, World Education Research Association

SIG Sessions

70.012. Graduate Student Breakfast. SIG-Critical Examination of Race, Ethnicity, Class and Gender in Education; Reception
Westin Bonaventure, Level 3, Hollywood Ballroom; 8:00-9:15am

Chair: Alexis Morgan Young, Michigan State University

Participants: Zora Haque, Harvard University; Rolonda L. Payne, University of Maryland; Maria O'Connor, Texas Christian University; Cambria Conley, University of Maryland; Marci Matsushita-Sanchez, California State University, Office of the Chancellor; Kemeyawi Wahpepah, Harvard University; Justin A. Coles, University of Massachusetts - Amherst; Lindsay Pérez Huber, California State University - Long

Beach; Venus E. Evans-Winters, The Ohio State University

70.013. George Washington University Forum Democracy & Education - Session 2. Affiliated Groups; Panel Discussion
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, San Bernardino; 8:00am to 5:00pm

70.014. Routledge Editorial Meetings (Day 2). Affiliated Groups; Board Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Level 2, Silver Lake; 8:00am to 5:00pm

70.015. Society of Professors of Education Annual Meeting. Affiliated Groups; Seminar
Westin Bonaventure, Level 3, Emerald Bay; 8:00am to 5:00pm

70.016. Teachers College Record Board Meeting/Voice Recording. Affiliated Groups; Board Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Level 3, Santa Monica A; 8:00am to 7:00pm

Saturday, April 11th, 8:45 am

Division Sessions

71.010. Division I Professional Faculty Development Community Meeting (Closed Meeting). Division I - Education in the Professions; Board Meeting
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 408A;
8:45-9:45am
Chairs: Linette P. Ross, National Board of Medical Examiners; Kadian McIntosh, University of Arizona; Carol A. Carman, University of Texas Medical Branch at Galveston
Participants: James L Huff, University of Georgia; Patricia S. O'Sullivan, University of California - San Francisco; LuAnn Wilkerson, University of Texas at Austin; Violet Kulo, University of Maryland - Baltimore; Ara Tekian, University of Illinois at Chicago; Gareth Gingell, Dell Medical School

Saturday, April 11th, 9:00 am

72.010. Editorial Board Meeting for the Journal of Negro Education. Affiliated Groups; Board Meeting
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 6th Floor, Century; 9:00am to 12:00pm

Saturday, April 11th, 9:45 am

Governance Meetings and Events

73.001. AERA Annual Meeting Policies and Procedures

Committee: Closed Meeting. AERA Governance;
Governance Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 513;
9:45-11:15am

Chair: *Carolyn D. Herrington, Florida State University*

73.002. Journal Publications Committee: Closed Meeting.

AERA Governance; Governance Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 514;
9:45-11:15am

Chair: *Peter A. Youngs, University of Virginia*

Presidential Sessions

73.010. Cultivating Change through Critical Imagination and Collective Liberation in Childhood. AERA Presidential Session; Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Beyond Disimagination: Critical Imagination as Framework for Liberatory Childhood Education. *Betzabe Torres Olave, University of Leeds*

Critical Imagination as Cultural Practice: Children's Storytelling and Meaning-Making Across Educational Contexts. *Belinda Mendelowitz, University of the Witwatersrand*

Transformative Agency in Early Learning: Children's Critical Imagination Across Educational Contexts. *Marilyn Fleer, Monash University*

Joy as Liberation: Critical Imagination and Youth-Led Participatory Research in Urban Education. *Ayana Allen-Handy, Hofstra University*

Decolonizing Imagination: Critical Ethnic Studies and Children's Agency in Elementary Classrooms. *Carolina Valdez, California State University - Fullerton*

Chairs: *Nicol R. Howard, Chapman University; Kira J. Carbonneau, Washington State University*

Discussant: *Stephanie R. Toliver, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

73.011. New and Emerging Histories of Education in the American West and Pacific. AERA Presidential Session; Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 404AB;

9:45-11:15am

Chair: *I. Jonna Perillo, University of Texas - El Paso*

Discussant: *I. Jonna Perillo, University of Texas - El Paso*

Panelists: *Michael Hines, Stanford University; Derek Taira, University of Hawai'i at Mānoa; Gonzalo Guzmán, Macalester College; Matthew G. Kelly, University of Washington; Laura K. Munoz, University of Nebraska - Lincoln*

73.012. Reimagining Educational Possibilities for Immigrant-Origin Students in an Era of Exclusion. AERA Presidential Session; Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 406AB;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Framing the Issue. *Carola Suarez-Orozco, Harvard University*
Taking A Historical Perspective. *Erika Lee, Harvard University*
The Chilling Effects of Deportations in Schools. *Jongyeon Joy Ee, Loyola Marymount University*

Implications of Social Exclusion and Learning. *Lisa Fortuna, University of California - Riverside*

Community Schooling Approaches. *Karen Hunter Quartz, University of California - Los Angeles*

Schools as Sanctuary Spaces. *Chandler Patton Miranda, Molloy University*

Chair: *Carola Suarez-Orozco, Harvard University*

Discussant: *Paola Uccelli, Harvard University*

AERA Research and Science Policy Sessions

73.013. The Leadership Role and Research Priorities of the National Science Foundation (NSF) STEM Education Directorate (EDU): A Conversation With James L. Moore III, NSF EDU Assistant Director. AERA Science and Policy Sessions; Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 409AB;
9:45-11:15am

Chair: *Anne-Marie Nunez, University of Texas - El Paso*

Speaker: *James L. Moore, National Science Foundation*

AERA Sessions

73.014. The Revision of the Testing Standards: Applications (Invited Joint AERA/NCME Session). AERA Sessions

Cosponsored with NCME; Invited Speaker Session
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor,
Wilshire Grand Ballroom III; 9:45-11:15am

Chair: *Ye Tong, National Board of Medical Examiners*

Participants: *Frank C. Worrell, University of California - Berkeley; Nathan Kuncel, University of Minnesota; Ellen E. Forte, edCount, LLC; Laura S. Hamilton, National Center*

for the Improvement of Educational Assessment, Inc.;
Kristen L. Huff, Curriculum Associates

Discussant: *Andy Reyes, University of Massachusetts - Boston*

Committee Sessions

73.015. Division J Fireside Chat: Unwriting the Hidden Curriculum: Unforgetting Histories, Reimagining Doctoral Futures. Graduate Student Council Cosponsored with Division J - Postsecondary Education; Invited Speaker Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 402A;
9:45-11:15am
Chair: *Gaurav Harshe, University of South Carolina*
Presenters: *Janay Georgetta Crosland, North Carolina State University; Sarah A. Hale, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

73.016. Recovering the Third World Studies Project: Towards New Visions of Anti-Imperial Pedagogies & Global Solidarities. International Relations Committee; Invited Speaker Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 501C;
9:45-11:15am
Participants:
Policing in British and American Schools: Tracing the Educational Legacies of Empire. *Derron Wallace, Brandeis University*
Palestine, Third World Solidarities, and Projects of Educational Justice. *Shirin Vossoughi, Northwestern University; Christopher Jadallah, University of California - Los Angeles*
Decolonial Education as Contradiction: Development, Dispossession & Contested Visions of Indigenous Futures in Western India. *Karishma Desai, Rutgers University*
The Lost Archive of Liberation: Lotus and the Palestinian Place in Afro-Asian Internationalism. *Chandni Desai, University of Toronto*
Coalition Building at Canadian Universities, Black Radical Thought and “Third World” Liberation. *rosalind hampton, University of Toronto - OISE*
Chair: *Krystal Strong, Rutgers University*
Discussant: *Linda T. Smith, Te Whare Wananga o Awanuiarangi*

International Organization Sessions

73.017. Two Decades of Academic Optimism: Exploring Its Legacy and Future for School Effectiveness and Equity. International Aligned Organizations/European Association for Research on Learning and Instruction - EARLI; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum B; 9:45-11:15am
Participants:

Building Equitable and Effective Schools. A Systematic Review of two decades of Academic Optimism Research. *Ruud Lelieur, University of Antwerp*
The relationship between academic futility, mathematic achievement, and academic optimism in the Czech education system. *Jana Straková, Charles University in Prague; Jaroslava Simonová, Charles University in Prague*
Teams as Carriers of Academic Optimism: Validation within Team-Based Professional Learning. *Hannah Bolten, University of Zurich; Beat Rechsteiner, University of Zurich; Flurin Gotsch, University of Zurich; Andrea Wullschlegler, University of Applied Sciences and Arts Northwestern Switzerland; Katharina Maag Merki, University of Zurich*
Chair: *Ruud Lelieur, University of Antwerp*
Discussant: *Jason Hsinchieh Wu, National Dong Hwa University*

Division Sessions

73.018. Developing Political Leadership among K-12 Public School Leaders: Imagining a Future of Research-Based Tools. Division A - Administration; Symposium
Westin Bonaventure, Level 2, Echo Park; 9:45-11:15am
Participants:
Political Leadership Tool #1: Fieldbook for Communities of Practice. *Jennifer Cheatham, Harvard University*
Political Leadership Tool #2: Interactive Online Simulations. *Rachel Sue White, University of Texas at Austin; Julie A. Marsh, University of Southern California*
Political Leadership Tool #3: Case Study. *Judy L. Pace, University of San Francisco*
Chair: *Julie A. Marsh, University of Southern California*
Discussant: *Caitlikn Sullivan, Leading Now*

73.019. Gender, Identity, and Intersectionality In Educational Leadership. Division A - Administration; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, La Brea; 9:45-11:15am
Participants:
“There's No Way to Make it Without Your People:” Documenting the Path to Leadership for Women of Color. *George Theoharis, Syracuse University; Eliani Jimenez Merino, Syracuse University; Vera Wang, Syracuse University*
Intersectional Agency: Three Latina School Principals in Chicago Public Schools. *Nancy Vegas, Northwestern University*
Chair: *Judy A. Alston, Miami University (OH)*
Discussant: *Lauren P. Bailes, University of Delaware*

73.020. Unforgetting Settler Colonial Histories of Science and Mathematics Education. Division B - Curriculum Studies; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304A;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

The Colonial Legacy of European Mathematics in the Americas: Baroque, Creole, Mixed. *Nathalie Sinclair, Simon Fraser University; Elizabeth De Freitas, Adelphi University*

Colonized Through Math: Native Erasure and Land Dispossession in Settler Colonial US Boarding School Curricula. *José Francisco Gutiérrez, University of Utah; Charles Sepulveda, The University of Utah; Cynthia Benally, University of Utah; Kēhaulani Vaughn, University of California - Riverside; Julie Sherman, University of California - Santa Barbara; Mary Smith, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Schools as Experiment Stations: Conceptualizing Science Through Plantation Pedagogy. *Bayley J. Marquez, University of Maryland*

Laboratories of Humanization: How Settler Colonial Techniques Prescribed Separate, Unequal US Science Educations. *Kathryn Lewkowitz Kirchgasser, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Chair: *Cynthia Benally, University of Utah*

Discussant: *Daniel Morales-Doyle, University of Illinois at Chicago*

73.021. Worlding Otherwise: (Non)Spatial Refusals and Affective (Im)Possibilities. Division B - Curriculum Studies; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304B;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Imagine...: Abolitionist Worlding as Refusal of Educational Deathscapes and Necropolitics. *Boni Wozolek, Pennsylvania State University - Abington*

Non-Spaces in Educational Praxis. *Brad Bierdz, Georgia Southern University*

The Interaction between University Physical Library and Students' Learning: Based on Lefebvre's Spatial Production Theory. *LIBING CHEN, East China Normal University; Hao Lei, East China Normal University*

Chair: *Laura M. Jewett, University of Texas - Rio Grande Valley*

Discussant: *Jordan Corson, Stockton University*

73.022. Contextual Influences on Motivation: Values, Beliefs, and Situational Dynamics. Division C - Learning and Instruction Cosponsored with SIG-Motivation in Education; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Santa Barbara C; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Environmental Values Moderate How Teacher Support Predicts Science Motivation. *Minghui Wang, University of California - Riverside; Valerie Backstrom, Riverside Unified School District; Linda Christopher, Galt Joint Union High School District; William Porter, University of California - Riverside; Cecilia Cheung, University of California -*

Riverside

Exploring the Congruence and Discrepancy Between Self-Efficacy and Utility Value in Predicting Adolescents' Academic Outcomes: A Study Using Polynomial Regression and Response Surface Analysis. *Chen Jing, East China Normal University; Linjia Zhang, East China Normal University; Yi Jiang, East China Normal University*

Is Motivation Too Situational to Replicate? Examining Fluctuations in Motivation Across Demographic and Institutional Contexts. *Claudia C. Sutter, CourseKata; Delaram A. Totonchi, University of Virginia; Jamie DeCoster, University of Virginia; Chris S. Hulleman, University of Virginia; Kenn E. Barron, James Madison University*

Longitudinal Development of Science Interest and Self-Efficacy and Their Post-College Outcomes. *Saki Inoue, Michigan State University; William Van Luven, Michigan State University; Utku Caybas, Michigan State University; Garam A. Lee, Michigan State University; Marissa N Taylor, University of Michigan; Tony Perez, Old Dominion University; Lisa Linnenbrink-Garcia, Michigan State University*

Multilevel Insights into Motivation, Multitasking, and Engagement: A Situated Expectancy Value Theory Perspective. *En Pei Huang, National Yang Ming Chiao Tung University; Tzu Hsuan Huang, National Yang Ming Chiao Tung University; Meng-Ting Lo, National Yang Ming Chiao Tung University*

Chair: *Delaram A. Totonchi, University of Virginia*

Discussant: *Kristy A. Robinson, McGill University*

73.023. Learning to Use Science to Build Just and Sustainable Futures. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Structured Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 515A;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

1. Developing Layperson Scientific Literacy Skills in High School Science Classrooms (Poster 1). *Huma Hussain-Abidi, Rutgers University; Clark A. Chinn, Rutgers University; Susan A. Yoon, University of Pennsylvania; Noora Fatima Noushad, University of Pennsylvania; Claire LeBovidge, University of Pennsylvania*
2. From Data to Civic Action: High School Students Investigate Socioscientific Issues through Air Quality Analysis (Poster 2). *Jooeun Shim, Teachers College, Columbia University; Susan A. Yoon, University of Pennsylvania*
3. Assessing Students' Ability to Develop Integrated Explanations of Social Justice Science Issues (Poster 3). *Kelly R. Billings, University of California - Berkeley; Weiyang Li, University of California - Berkeley; Allison Bradford, University of California - Berkeley; Marcia Linn, University of California - Berkeley*
4. Designing for Worldmaking in High School Chemistry

through Research Practice Partnership (Poster 4). *Qiu Zhong, University of California - Irvine; Hosun Kang, University of California - Irvine*

5. Learning Biodiversity, Living Sustainably: CASE Project Impacts on Biodiversity Understanding and Actions (Poster 5). *Katherine Joy Nilsen, WestEd; Aaron Soo Ping Chow, WestEd; Sara Salisbury, WestEd; Ashley Iveland, WestEd*
6. Learning Climate Change: An Experimental Study Exploring the Role of Design Activities and Artificial Intelligence (Poster 6). *Ibrahim Delen, Usak University; Nisa Nur Karabacak, Bogazici University; Zeynep Gül Dertli, Hacettepe University; Bora Senceylan, Istanbul University; Esra Kahraman, Usak University; Hakan Akcay, Bogazici University; Bahadır Yildiz, Hacettepe University; Gokhan Ince, Istanbul Technical University*
7. The CASE for Community-Centered Science Education (Poster 7). *Katherine Joy Nilsen, WestEd; Aaron Soo Ping Chow, WestEd; Sara Salisbury, WestEd; Ashley Iveland, WestEd*
8. Thinking As Engaged Citizens: A Civic Science Approach to Foster Elementary Students' Informed Civic Decision-Making (Poster 8). *wenxiang lu, The Ohio State University; Kevin Fulton, The Ohio State University; Gukyeong Eom, The Ohio State University; Tzu-Jung Lin, The Ohio State University; Li-Ching Hung, National Taiwan Normal University; Michael Glassman, The Ohio State University; Eric M. Anderman, The Ohio State University*

Chair: *Imogen Herrick, University of Kansas*

Discussant: *Asli Sezen-Barrie, University of California - Irvine*

73.024. Making Technology Work for You: A Show-and-Tell of Practical Tools for Educational Researchers.

Division C - Learning and Instruction; Invited Speaker Session
Westin Bonaventure, Level 3, Avalon; 9:45-11:15am

Chairs: *Rebecca Myers, Montclair State University; Micaha Dean Hughes, North Carolina State University*

Participants: *Michele Wiedemer, Southern Methodist University; Hilal Ayan, Florida State University; Lizeth Sandoval, Pepperdine University; Shaun Bennett, North Carolina State University*

73.025. The Reduction of Differences in Early Vocabulary.

Division C - Learning and Instruction; Symposium
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, La Cienega; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Which words to teach? Unpacking results from an effective vocabulary intervention for children with SLI. *Barbara Wasik, Temple University; Annemarie Hindman, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*

Efficacy of Vocabulary Instruction Embedded in Prerecorded Story Books for Preschoolers. *Howard Goldstein, University of South Florida; Elizabeth Kelley, University of Missouri; Lindsey Peters-Sanders, University of South Florida; Jeffrey*

M. Williams, University of South Florida; Elizabeth Broome, University of South Florida

Early Vocabulary Acquisition: How Word Frequency, Sociodemographic Context, and Intervention Effects Shape First-Grade Growth. *Leonie Dargiewicz, Technische Universität Dortmund; Svenja Wehrhöfer, TU Dortmund University; Annika Ohle-Peters, TU Dortmund University; Ulrich Ludewig, TU Dortmund University; Nele McElvany, TU Dortmund University; Fani Lauer mann, University of Bonn*

Guided Drawing with Multilingual Preschoolers: A Research-Based Approach to Vocabulary and Concept Acquisition. *Christina Marie Cassano, Salem State University; Kathleen A. Paciga, Columbia College Chicago*

Chair: *Leonie Dargiewicz, Technische Universität Dortmund*
Discussant: *Doris Luft Baker, University of Texas at Austin*

73.026. Addressing Challenges in Causality: Free Will, Mediation and Latent Factors, Heterogeneity, and Variable Selection. Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Paper Session
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 6th Floor, Metropolitan; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Free Will as an Obstacle to Randomized Controlled Trials. *Jason Bryer, City University of New York; Angela M. Lui, CUNY - School of Professional Studies; Piet Wesling, University at Albany - SUNY; Heidi L. Andrade, University at Albany - SUNY*

Valid Instrumental Variable Selection for Causal Analysis. *Jiachen Liu, Michigan State University; Yuehua Cui, Michigan State University; Haolei Weng, Michigan State University; William H. Schmidt, Michigan State University*

Causal Machine Learning with Latent Factors. *Benjamin Kelcey, University of Cincinnati; Amota Ataneka, University of Cincinnati; Jean Baptiste Habarurema, University of Cincinnati*

Enhancing the Interpretability of Heterogeneous Treatment Effects using Kolmogorov Arnold Network. *Chenguang Pan, Teachers College, Columbia University; Yuxuan Li, Teachers College, Columbia University; Youmi Suk, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Familywise Type I Error Rates and Statistical Power in Causal Mediation Analysis with Multiple Mediators. *Xiao Liu, University of Texas at Austin; Jasmine Zeng, University of Texas at Austin*

Chair: *M. Shane Tutwiler, University of Rhode Island*

Discussant: *Kamal Chawla, University of Maine*

73.027. Overcoming Master Narratives: Unforgetting, Reimagining, and Reconstructing Through Quantitative Ethnography. Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Symposium

InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 7th Floor,

Hollywood Ballroom I; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Overcoming the assumption of Global North dominance, valuing contributions of the Global South. *Danielle Pascual Espino, Pepperdine University*

Navigating Tensions and Togetherness: A Quantitative Ethnographic Exploration of Black College Students' Intragroup Experiences. *Adaurennaya C. Onyewuenyi, The College of New Jersey*

Using Quantitative Ethnography to Model How Black Girls Develop Sociocritical AI Literacies. *Golnaz Arastoopour Irgens, Vanderbilt University*

Visualizing Racism: Towards a QuantCrit Epistemic Network Analysis. *Nichole M. Garcia, Rutgers University*

Chair: *Brendan R. Eagan, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Discussant: *Brendan R. Eagan, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

73.028. Liberation and Education: Historical Perspectives on Black Educational Thought. Division F - Historical Inquiry in Education; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 306A;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Nannie Helen Burroughs and the Early Rise of Womanism. *Traki L. Taylor, Bowie State University*

Mapping the Intellectual Genealogy of Carter Godwin Woodson. *Lasana D. Kazembe, Indiana University - Indianapolis*

Black Women's Ideas, White Philanthropy: Developing the First Generation of Black Women Scholars and Artists. *Linda Marie Perkins, Claremont Graduate University*

Re-Narrating the Experiences of Black Women Leaders in the Academy. *Deirdre Cobb-Roberts, University of South Florida; Talia Randa Esnard, University of the West Indies - St. Augustine; Maria Migueliz Valcarlos, Eastern New Mexico University*

Chairs: *Derrick Alridge, University of Virginia; Ronald E. Chennault, DePaul University*

Discussant: *Elizabeth Todd-Breland, University of Illinois at Chicago*

73.029. Remembering a Way Forward by Reclaiming the Past. Division F - Historical Inquiry in Education; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 501B;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

"If There is But One": The Legal Battle for Educational Access in Oklahoma. *Sara Doolittle, University of Central Oklahoma*

"Hallway Hoolliganism": Building a Justification for Police in New York City Schools, 1968-1972. *Ajua Kouadio, Rutgers University*

Getting in Grown Folks' Business: Reclaiming the Histories of Black Women Teachers through Endarkened Archival

Practice. *Asia S. Thomas, Augusta State University*

"It Was Never Less Than": Reclaiming Narratives through Student Counter-stories of Baltimore County's Colored Schools. *Brianna C. Ross, Morgan State University*
Using Social Network Analysis to Map Chicago's Black Artist-Educator Networks. *Debra Anne Hardy, University of Wisconsin - Milwaukee*

Chair: *Vincent D. Willis, University of Alabama*

Discussant: *Alexander D. Hyres, University of Utah*

73.030. Between Constraints and Possibilities: Narratives of Agency and Hope in Surveilled Educational Spaces. Division G - Social Context of Education; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304C;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Re/turning to the Roots of Progressive Education - Classrooms as Sites of Social Change. *Haeny S. Yoon, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Counternarratives of Inclusion: Exploring Disabled Youth Agency in Restrictive Educational Spaces. *Katherine Newhouse, New York University*

Exploring Alternatives: Alternative schools and metrics of success. *Adrienne Vitullo, Teachers College*

Teacher Education for What Comes Next. *Anne Burns Thomas, SUNY - College at Cortland*

Daily Becomings: Ethnography of the Humane within an Inhumane System. *Lalitha Vasudevan, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Chair: *Nancy L. Lesko, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Discussant: *Haeny S. Yoon, Teachers College, Columbia University*

73.031. Composing otherwise: Black Studies and the future of arts-based education research. Division G - Social Context of Education; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 306B;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Pedagogies of unsettling: Black feminist aesthetics and art education's hidden curricula. *gloria j. wilson, The Ohio State University*

Black othermothering, the arts, education, and a study designed by them for them. *K. Lynn Robinson, The Ohio State University*

Engaging the quiet: Black Matriarchal Archives and pedagogies of listening. *Sydney Summey, The Ohio State University*

Love's testimony: Critical arts-based inquiry as a third space and pedagogical concern. *Iyana Shanel Hill, The Ohio State University*

Chair: *gloria j. wilson, The Ohio State University*

Discussant: *K. Lynn Robinson, The Ohio State University*

73.032. Stepping into the (Cess)Pool While the Water Is

Stirring: Deconstructing/Reconstructing Black Pedagogical Activism Narratives. Division G - Social Context of Education; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 403B;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- Re-Membering Pedagogical Activism: Africana Research Methodologies in a Multi-State Youth-Led Lab. *Melissa Speight Vaughn, Georgia State University*
- Histories within Histories and an Eye to the Future: An Organizational Ethnography. *Max Altman, Southern Education Foundation; Allison Boyle, Southern Education Foundation, Inc.*
- Black Pedagogical Activism as Creative Praxis: Learning from the Jeanes Teachers to Imagine Educational Futures. *Camea Davis, Research Partnership for Professional Learning*
- Empowering Voices: The Role of Black Women Educators in Shaping Equitable Futures. *Danie Marshall, Georgia State University*
- Leaning into the Jeanes Teaching Tradition for Equity in Educational Research and Practice. *Terrance Joshua Lewis, University of Alabama*

Chair: *Joyce E. King, Georgia State University*

Discussant: *LaGarrett J. King, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

73.033. Faculty Roles in Transition: Navigating Generative AI in Doctoral Education. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Working Group Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 501A;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- Researching Generative AI Capabilities to Inform Doctoral Education. *Marilee Bresciani Ludvik, University of San Diego; Nydia C. Sánchez, University of San Diego; Erin Cooke, University of San Diego; Scott Harvey, University of San Diego*
- Cultural Dimensions of AI Integration: Working with Diverse Doctoral Students. *Nydia C. Sánchez, University of San Diego; Marilee Bresciani Ludvik, University of San Diego*

Chair: *Marilee Bresciani Ludvik, University of San Diego*

Discussant: *Nydia C. Sánchez, University of San Diego*

73.034. Who Leads, Who Labors, Who Lasts? Institutional Climate, Labor, and Leadership in Higher Education. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Plaza III;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- A Multivariate Analysis of Institutional Support, Campus Climate, and Women of Color Job Intentions. *Ana L. Romero, University of California - Los Angeles*
- Exploring Indigenous Women's Leadership Conceptualizations: Prompting Talking Circle Discussions using the Career Aspiration Survey Revised. *Christie G. Meninick*

Breaking Souls, Building Walls: How Gendered-Racialized Organizational Hierarchies Drive Women of Color from Higher Education. *M. Yvonne Taylor, Northwest Education Access*

"I'm Always on the Clock": Examining Black Women Student Leaders' Racialized Labor. *Juana Hollingsworth, Morgan State University*

Chair: *Seonmi Jin, Indiana University*

Discussant: *Ting-Han Chang, William Paterson University*

73.035. Beyond Traditional Methods: Innovative Approaches to Humanizing Mathematics in Teacher Preparation.

Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 8;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- Cooking Up Math: Exploring Early Childhood Pre-Service Teachers' Cooking Integration. *SeungJung Jo, SUNY - Geneseo*
- Family and Community Engagement: A Problem of Practice in Mathematics Teacher Education. *Regina M. Mistretta, Saint John's University*
- Good Books Are Good for Math: Enacting a Critical Math Read-Aloud with Preservice Teachers. *Heather Lindfors-Navarro, Northern Arizona University; Stephanie M Branson, Northern Arizona University*
- Leveraging Exposure and Experience to Support Teacher Candidates' Conceptions of Equitable Teaching. *Amanda Mohammad Mirzaei, Manhattanville University; Ethan P. Smith, Washington State University - Tri-Cities*
- Brushing the Surface: A Preservice Teacher's Journey of Rehumanizing Mathematics Through Iterative Art Integration. *Destiny Kuespert, Washington State University - Tri-Cities; Ethan P. Smith, Washington State University - Tri-Cities; Yichien Cooper, Washington State University - Tri-Cities*

Chair: *Keirah Comstock, University of Rochester*

Discussant: *Cathery Yeh, University of Texas at Austin*

73.036. Critical Counter-Narratives as Transformative Praxis in Urban Teaching and Learning. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum I;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- Expanding (and Moving Beyond) Conceptions of "Counter" in the Work of Narrative. *Rich Milner, Vanderbilt University*
- Unveiling a Communally Bonded Educational Ecosystem: A Dialogue Between Historical and Contemporary Black Educators. *Jerome E. Morris, University of Missouri - St. Louis; Nicole Misra, University of Missouri-St. Louis; Luimil Negrón, University of Missouri - St. Louis; Dionne Ferguson, Good Journey Development Foundation*

A Longitudinal and Critical Counter-Narrative of Literacy Learning for a Child Diagnosed with Aspergers. *Catherine F. Compton-Lilly, University of South Carolina*

Decriminalizing Children of Color: Critical Counternarratives from Preschool Teachers of Color. *Katrina Liu, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Richard C. Miller, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Arneitha F. Ball, Stanford University; Claire Therese Tredwell, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*

Young Children as Storytellers: Reframing Mobility, Multilingualism, and Transnational Childhoods. *Jungmin Kwon, Michigan State University; Patricia A. Edwards, Michigan State University*

Chairs: *Katrina Liu, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Patricia A. Edwards, Michigan State University; Richard C. Miller, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*

Discussant: *A. Lin Goodwin, Boston College*

73.037. Designing Professional Learning Communities That Center Educator Choice, Agency, and Well-Being.

Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 9;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

A Systematic Literature Review of Teacher Professional Development Through Co-Design. *Dongni Guo, University at Albany - SUNY; Aya M. Isaac, University at Albany - SUNY; Jianwei Zhang, University at Albany - SUNY; Thomas Underwood, University at Albany - SUNY; Lei Ding, University at Albany - SUNY; Alae Sherafat, University at Albany - SUNY*

Designing Teacher Learning: A Case Study of Professional Development Facilitators' Sensemaking and Collaborative Process. *Kayla Ueshiro, University of California - Irvine; Christina Kimmerling, University of California - Irvine; Rossella Santagata, University of California - Irvine*

Reframing Teacher Preparation Through the Lens of Well-being Literacy: A Sequential Mixed Methods Study. *Benita R. Brooks, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Borna Nemet, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Sinead Pelleschi, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Randall M Varner, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*

Self-Directed Professional Development: A Systematic Review of Research (2015–2025). *Zixi Li, Indiana University; Ge Tang, Teachers College, Columbia University; Zhou Zhang, Columbia University*

Which Types of Professional Learning Lead to Positive Change in Teaching Practice? *Ye-Ji Park, Hanyang University; Jeon-Yi Lee, Gyeonggi Institute of Education; Joo-Ho Park, Hanyang University*

Chair: *Niki Elliott, University of San Diego*

Discussant: *Helen M. Hazi, West Virginia University*

73.038. Educators at the Margins: Pathways of Belonging and

Resistance. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 7;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Braiding Identities: Testimonios of Culturally Diverse Educators in Early Childhood Education. *Maria J. Ruiz-Martinez, University of Colorado - Boulder; Margaret Bartlett, University of Wisconsin - Milwaukee; Leanne M. Evans, University of Wisconsin - Milwaukee*

Fugitive Moves: Black Educators' Sense-Making and Escapes. *Sciatta R Padmore, University of Washington*

Metis Teachers' Perspectives: Recruitment, Mentorship and Retention. *laura forsythe, University of Winnipeg; Lucy Delgado, University of Manitoba*

Teaching across Communities: Immigrant Teachers Navigating Identity and Belonging in a Chinese Heritage Language School. *Yiting Chu, University of South Florida - Tampa; Yuechen Sun, University of South Carolina; Wenyu Guo, University of South Florida; Min Yu, Wayne State University*

Chair: *Maria J. Ruiz-Martinez, University of Colorado - Boulder*

Discussant: *Margarita Bianco, University of Colorado - Denver*

73.039. Equity in the Crosshairs: Leadership, Closure, and Advocacy in Contentious Times.

Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 1;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Approaches to Equity Leadership in Three U.S. School Districts: Racial-Historical Contexts in Neoconservative Times. *Decoteau J. Irby, University of Illinois at Chicago; Ann M. Ishimaru, University of Washington*

Educational Opportunity Amid Urban Revitalization: Perceptions from Long-term Resident Parents and Children. *Tara Blagg, University of Southern California; Bianca Burch, Wayne State University; Kara S. Finnigan, University of Michigan; Huriya Jabbar, University of Southern California; DeMarcus A Jenkins, University of Pennsylvania; Sarah Winchell Lenhoff, Wayne State University; Jeremy L. Singer, University of Michigan-Flint; Tyra Timm, University of Texas at Austin*

Exploring the Survival of Historically Black Schools Amid Recurrent Waves of School Closures. *Ja'Nya Banks, University of California - Berkeley*

Black School Choice as Refusal: The Political Context of Black Families' School Choice. *De'Ja Wood, Vanderbilt University*

Argument, Equity, and Public Narrative: Lessons from Anti-Voucher Advocacy. *Tabitha Reynolds Hoang, Southern Education Foundation; Darian A. Burns, Southern Education Foundation; Max Altman, Southern Education Foundation; Allison Boyle, Southern Education Foundation, Inc.; Fred A. Jones, Southern Education Foundation*

Chair: *Marlinda Boxley, Bowie State University*

Discussant: *Brittany C. Murray, Davidson College*

73.040. Science of Reading Legislation's Effects and Their Mechanisms: Studies of Legislation from Three States.

Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond
10; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

A Mississippi Miracle? The Effect of Mississippi's Science-of-Reading Reforms on Elementary Reading Skills. *Paul T. Von Hippel, University of Texas at Austin*

K-5 Teachers' Knowledge, Beliefs, and Practice: Influence of Science of Reading PD in North Carolina. *Paola Pilonieta, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Erin K. Washburn, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Alicia Stewart Kitten, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Brittany Simone Hart, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Helen Rose Miesner, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*

Reading Reform in Action: MTSS Implementation Across Differing School Performance Trends in Kentucky. *Sangbaek Park, University of Louisville; Jennifer R. Pollard, University of Louisville; Jennifer Fosbinder, University of Louisville*

Patterns in Literacy Curriculum Adoption and Low-SES Upper Elementary Reading Achievement: Preliminary Findings from California. *Jacob Rowley, University of Southern California*

Chair: *Erin K. Hogan, University of Louisville*

Discussant: *Deborah K. Reed, University of Tennessee*

73.041. The School-Prison Nexus: Causes and Effects.

Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 2;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Examining the Role of K-12 School Instability Among Formerly Incarcerated College Students. *Cynthia Valencia-Ayala, University of California - San Francisco*

Hardening Schools, Targeting Students: Minoritized Students, School Security, and the School-Prison Nexus. *Samantha L. Viano, George Mason University*

Harsher Punishments, Lesser Infractions: Disciplinary Injustice for Native American Students in New Mexico Public Schools. *Amy Watson-Grace, The Ohio State University; Hexin Yang, The Ohio State University; Gia Barboza Salerno, The Ohio State University*

Out of School but in the Home: National Evidence on How School Discipline Impacts Parents. *Chris Curran, University of Florida; Jiyeon Goo, University of Florida; Julie Gerlinger, University of Oklahoma*

The Role of Trauma-Informed Instructional Strategies on Educational Outcomes for Incarcerated Youth in U.S. Prisons. *Rizwan Shaikh, Texas A&M University-Corpus*

Christi; James Ikonopoulos, Texas A&M University - Corpus Christi

Chair: *Natasha N. Johnson, Augusta University*

Discussant: *Tanishia Lavette Williams, Brandeis University*

SIG Sessions

73.042. Participatory Action Research Projects at Hispanic-Serving Institutions: Co-creating HSI-PAR to Foster Servingness and Community-Centered Transformation.

SIG-Action Research; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum F;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Leading with ESPARiTU: Recovering the Origins of Serving through a Student Participatory Action Research Project in a Grassroots HSRI. *Arlene Cano Matute, University of California - Riverside; Alexis Meza, University of California - Berkeley*

Transforming Hispanic Serving Institutions through Student Voice. *Amber Michelle Gonzalez, California State University - Sacramento; Kevin Ferreira van Leer, University of Connecticut*

Participatory Action Research as a Servingness Structure for Latinx Undocumented College Students at Hispanic-Serving Institutions. *Cinthya Salazar, University of California - Los Angeles*

Documenting the Transformative Experiences of Latinas at an HSI through a Chicana Feminist PAR Study. *Ruth María López, University of Arizona*

Transforming Hispanic Serving Community Colleges Using Participatory Action Research. *Gina Ann Garcia, University of California - Berkeley; Flor Huerta, Fullerton College; Julio Rene Flores, Santa Rosa Junior College*

Chair: *Cynthia D. Villarreal, Northern Arizona University*

Discussants: *Marcela G. Cuellar, University of California - Davis; Louie F. Rodriguez, University of California - Riverside*

73.043. Moving Toward Liberation: Somatic, Decolonial, and Queer Pedagogies in Dance Education.

SIG-Arts and Inquiry in the Visual and Performing Arts in Education; Demonstration/Performance
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 411
(Theatre); 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Rituals of Survival: A Queer, Embodied Praxis of Refusal and Reworlding. *Aleta Brown, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*

Free To Be Me! Andean Dance Performance Demonstration for Decoloniality and Movement. *Ambika Gopal Raj, California State University - Los Angeles; Alicia Moseley, Cal State Los Angeles*

Somatic Pedagogies for Creativity in Dance Education and

Research. *Traci Klein, McGill University*

Chair: *Stephanie Anne Shelton, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*

73.044. Shaping Local-to-Global Futures: Expanding the Boundaries of Bi-/multilingual Education Research. SIG-Bilingual Education Research Cosponsored with SIG-Second Language Research; Invited Speaker Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 502A;
9:45-11:15am

Chair: *Ana Celia Zentella, University of California - San Diego*

Panelists: *Ester J. de Jong, University of Colorado - Denver; Christian J. Faltis, Texas A&M International University; Antonieta Heyden Megale, Unifesp - Federal University of São Paulo; Jeff MacSwan, University of Maryland; Josefina V. Tinajero, University of Texas - El Paso*

Facilitator: *Cristian R. Aquino-Sterling, Texas Tech University; Suzanne García, California State University - Monterey Bay*

73.045. Preserving Spirit and Self: Narratives of Black Educational Renewal. SIG-Caribbean and African Studies in Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum G; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Examining Indigenous Knowledge as New Visions for Education in a Remote Rural Community in Jamaica.
Shereca Shelly-Ann McGowan-Hunter, University of the West Indies - Mona

Purposeful Attention to Preserving Our Spirit: Afro-Caribbean Women in K-20 Resisting Erasure.
Shalander L. Samuels, Kean University; Amanda Wilkerson, University of Central Florida; Sherika S. Dacres, School District of Osceola County

Unforgetting Histories: Black Immigrant Youth and Narratives of Identity Reconstruction.
Neisha Terry Young, Stony Brook University - SUNY

“We’re Forgotten”: African Immigrant Girls’ Experiences in PreK-12 Education.
Ogechi Ironi, University of Pittsburgh

Chair: *Shawn S. Savage, University of North Carolina - Wilmington*

Discussant: *Oluwaseun Oyindamola Ogunleye, University of Michigan*

73.046. Illuminating Instruction and Assessment to Support Student Success in Higher Education: International Perspectives. SIG-Classroom Assessment; Symposium
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Los Feliz; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Investigating Students’ Experiences and Instructional Change in Undergraduate STEM Instruction and Assessment: A Mixed-Methods Study.
Dustin Sonny James Van Orman, Western Washington University; Dan Hanley, Western

Washington University; Josie Melton, Western Washington University; Greta Moses, Western Washington University; Sophie Westermann, Western Washington University; Anna Manry, Western Washington University; Alexis Marquez, University of Texas, Rio Grande Valley; Morgan Stucky, Western Washington University; Sophie Baughn, Western Washington University

The Impact of Active Learning on Student Course Performance in STEM Varies by Type and Intensity: A Meta-Analysis.
Elli Theobald, University of Washington; Shangmou Xu, University of Washington

Addressing Challenges and Finding Opportunities: Assessment in Higher Education.
Christopher DeLuca, Queen's University - Kingston; Katrina Carbone, Queen's University - Kingston

How and When Does Self-Assessment Impact Achievement? A Moderated Mediation Model Examining the Role of Effort and Feedback Literacy.
Norman B. Mendoza, The Education University of Hong Kong; Zi Yan, The Education University of Hong Kong

Longitudinal Shifts in Spanish University Assessment: Continuity and Emerging Patterns.
Ernesto Panadero, Dublin City University; Javier Fernández-Ruiz, Universidad Autónoma de Madrid; Juan Fraile, Fundación Universidad Francisco de Vitoria; Alaitz Amezcua, Universidad de Deusto; Carlos Felipe Rodríguez-Hernández, New Jersey Institute of Technology

Chairs: *Dustin Sonny James Van Orman, Western Washington University; Ernesto Panadero, Dublin City University*

Discussant: *Heidi L. Andrade, University at Albany - SUNY*

73.047. Remaining Critical in the Midst of (Neo)Colonial Censorship. SIG-Critical Educators for Social Justice; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 504;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

A Settler’s Journey of Decolonization in Hawai’i to Inform Social Justice Pedagogies.
Phillippe Rivera Fernandez-Brennan, Halau Ku Mana

Counterstorytelling Teacher Retention: How Teachers of Color Conceptualize Staying in Educational Spaces.
Sarah Day Dayon, University of Michigan

The Double Bind of District-Institutionalized Racial Affinity Spaces for Teachers of Color.
Emily Dech, University of California - Riverside; Verna Wong, University of Minnesota; Angelina Momanyi, University of Minnesota

Teacher Perspectives on Implementing Project-Based Learning in a Regressive Educational Climate.
Hilary Simpson, University of Michigan; Kat McRitchie, University of Michigan

Teachers’ Enactment of Racially Just Pedagogy in an Era of Fascism and Educational Censorship.
Bernardette Josee Pinetta, University of California - Riverside; Russell Stoll,

Community Partner

Chair: *Bernardette Josee Pinetta, University of California - Riverside*

Discussant: *Diana Bonilla, Northern Illinois University*

73.048. Centering the Voices of Black Women and Girls in English Education. SIG-Critical Examination of Race, Ethnicity, Class and Gender in Education; Symposium JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Atrium II; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Embodied Knowledge: The Lived Experiences of Black Disabled Women. *Elena Darling-Hammond, Stanford University*

No Shelter in the Time of Storm: A Black Womanist Inquiry into Teaching, Studying, and Surviving in Higher Education. *Vivett Cereta Hemans Dukes, Teachers College, Columbia University*

A Critical Exploration of the Experiences of Black Women Secondary English Teachers in New York City Public Schools. *Lakisha Odum, Queens College - CUNY*

Having Our Say: Black Girls Speaking Back to Their Teachers. *Stephanie Robillard, St. Mary's College of California*

Chair: *Stephanie Robillard, St. Mary's College of California*
Discussant: *Yolanda Sealey-Ruiz, Teachers College, Columbia University*

73.049. Emancipatory Pro-Black and Pro-Latinx Reading Research and Teaching. SIG-Critical Perspectives on Early Childhood Education; Symposium Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 301A; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

"I Am the Universe" Toward a Reader Model that Centers Culture. *Roderick Peele, Northern Parkway School; Kindel Turner Nash, Appalachian State University*

Book Expansion for Language and Linguistic Justice. *Leah Panther, Mercer University; Rosana Sanchez, Mercer University; Lucy Gitonga, Mercer University*

Unforgetting Histories & Nurturing Futures: What Mamá Gallina Teaches Literacy Educators about Healing Bilingualities. *Kimberly Muñoz, Universidad Autónoma del Estado de Hidalgo; Alexandra Babino, Texas Woman's University*

Deepening Explorations of Racial and Linguistic Representation in Picturebooks through Critical Translingual Literacies. *Angie Zapata, University of Missouri; Adrianna González Ybarra, The University of Texas Rio Grande Valley*

Black is Beauty: Jamaican Teachers Fostering Pro-Blackness in Elementary Education. *Jarvais J Jackson, Indiana University Indianapolis*

Why Early Literacy Research in Spanish-dominant countries Matters. *Lucinda A. Soltero-Gonzalez, University of*

Colorado - Denver; Cristina Gillanders, University of Colorado - Denver

Chair: *Eliza G. Braden, University of South Carolina*

Discussants: *Roberta P. Gardner, Kennesaw State University; Navan Govender, University of Strathclyde; Claudia Rodriguez-Mojica, University of California - Davis; Allison Briceno, San José State University; Rachael E. Gabriel, University of Connecticut; Sanjuana Carrillo Rodriguez, Kennesaw State University*

73.050. Critical Posthuman and Postfoundational Methodological Configurations. SIG-Critical Posthuman and Postfoundational Studies in Education; Paper Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum C; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Beyond Linear Learning: Service-Learning as Complex Assemblage in Teacher Education. *Celina Salvador-Garcia, University Jaume I; Kathryn J. Strom, California State University - East Bay; Erica Eva Colmenares, San Jose State University*

Haunting Whiteness in Teaching: Ghostly Residue of the Palimpsest School Space. *Maddie Neufeld, Teachers College, Columbia University*

The Generativity of Deviant Collaboration. *Asilia K. Franklin-Phipps, SUNY - College at New Paltz; Tristan G. Gleason, California State Polytechnic University - Humboldt*

Time Travel Methods: Queering Time and Space in Critical Qualitative Inquiry. *Laura Elizabeth Smithers, University of Nevada, Reno*

Unsettling the Humanist Teacher Education: Posthuman and Decolonial Figurations of Practice. *Francesca Bracci, University of Florence; Loretta Fabbri, University of Siena; Mario Giampaolo*

Chair: *Ezra Gouvea, Rethink Learning Labs*

Discussant: *Mirka E. Koro, Arizona State University*

73.051. Toward Anti-Imperial Thought in Education: Pedagogy, Methodology, and Struggle for a World Anew. SIG-Decolonial, Postcolonial, and Anti-Colonial Studies in Education; Symposium Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 303B; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Reading Archives and Writing Colonial Histories: Methodological Approaches to US Colonial Education in the Philippines. *Roland Sintos Coloma, Wayne State University*

Education by Movement: School Restructuring, Racial Capitalism, and the Black Radical Tradition in Rural Detroit. *Ezekiel Joubert, California State University - Los Angeles*

Deconstructing King's "Beyond Vietnam": Pedagogy, Decolonial Thought, and Internationalism during the Vietnam Era. *Kevin D. Lam, Drake University*

Du Bois and Ambedkar: Discourse on Race and Caste. *Kamau*

Rashid, Northeastern Illinois University

Chair: *Kevin D. Lam, Drake University*

Discussant: *Antonia Darder, Loyola Marymount University*

73.052. Writing, Righting, and Rioting Against Colonial-Carceral Machineries: School Abolition in Real Life, Time, and Context. SIG-Decolonial, Postcolonial, and Anti-Colonial Studies in Education; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 303A;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Building Abolitionist Futures of Education with NYC Black, Latine, and Working-Class Community Organizers of Color. *Sohini Das, New York University*

“We Demand Total Control of Our Schools!”: 1960s Community Control Movement as Black Abolitionist World-Building. *Imani C. Wilson, New York University*

Imagining Alternatives: Young Black Voices on Discipline, Value, and Community in Education. *Alexandrea R. Henry, Stanford University*

Prison Break: Black-male-centered Educational Spaces, Gender Abolition, and Gender Self-determination. *Gene F. McAdoo, University of California - Los Angeles*

Chair: *Brian Cabral, University of Texas at Austin*

Discussant: *David O. Stovall, University of Illinois at Chicago*

73.053. Investigating Generative AI Use and Integration in International Contexts: Opportunities, Challenges, and Insights. SIG-International Studies; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 309;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

The Role of Artificial Intelligence for Sustainable Development: A Systematic Literature Review. *Birol Bulut, University of California - Los Angeles; Fadhila Hadjeris, University of California - Los Angeles*

Integrating AI into EFL Education in the Arab World: A Systematic Review. *Raghad Faisal Alsaka, University of Idaho; Nesma Ragab Nasr, Northern Arizona University*

Bridging Digital and Linguistic Divides: Piloting AI-Powered Personalized Learning in Rural India. *Zainab Azim, Harvard University; Ranjitsinh Disale, Harvard University*

Let’s Talk About AI: Analyzing International Students’ Narratives on Reddit. *Samaa Haniya, Pepperdine University; Carolyn Musyimi-Kamau, Pepperdine University*

ESL Writing Pedagogy in the Age of Artificial Intelligence: Voices of International Students’ from the Global South. *Fadhila Hadjeris, University of California - Los Angeles; Kathy Yi-Hang Li, UCLA*

Chair: *Weijian Yan, Idaho State University*

Discussant: *Harry O’Neil, University of Southern California*

73.054. Intersection of STEM and Educational Leadership: AI, Virtual Learning, and STEM Outcomes. SIG-Leadership

for School Improvement; Paper Session

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Los Cerritos; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Elementary School Leadership Practices and Dispositions in Strengthening Students’ STEM Interests and Capabilities: A Meta-Synthesis. *Richard Baah-Mintah, University of Alabama; Jingping Sun, University of Alabama; Fredrick Oteng Agyeman, University of Alabama; Angela D. Benson, University of Alabama; Chidinma Nwafor Kalu, University of Alabama; Richard Anietie, University of Alabama*

A Quasi-Experimental Study of Emotional Intelligence Interventions and Effects on Principals’ Leadership Behaviors and Professional Learning Communities. *Zan Li, The Education University of Hong Kong; Junjun Chen, Education University of Hong Kong*

The Impact of Virtual Mentor Coaching on School Leaders’ Knowledge of Turnaround Strategies. *Jordan Donop, Texas A&M University; Mohammad Taheri, Texas A&M University; Beverly J. Irby, Texas A&M University; Cindy L. Guerrero, Texas A&M University; Linda Rodriguez, Texas A&M University; Rafael Lara-Alecio, Texas A&M University; Fuhui Tong, Texas A&M University*

Unforgetting the Past, Futuring AI: Leadership Visions for Equitable Educational Technologies. *Veysel Altunel, Louisiana State University; Stacy-Ann Campbell, Louisiana State University; Henderson Lewis, Louisiana State University*

Unpacking AI Pre-Adoption Appraisal of School Principals Using PLS-SEM. *Zichen Zhao, Ningbo University; Chengming Zhang, Ningbo University; Weidong Wu, Zhejiang International Studies University; Min Hu, Zhejiang International Studies University; Xiao Wu, Zhejiang International Studies University; Baoge Zhang, Ningbo University*

Discussants: *Anastasia Shikanova, The Ohio State University; Itauma Itauma, Northwood University*

73.055. Disassembling Mis/Disinformation, Reassembling Democracy: Theory, Practice, and Possibilities. SIG-Media, Culture, and Learning; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Georgia I;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

The Politics of Mis/Disinformation: Ideological Asymmetries in Media Practice and Process. *Alexandra Thrall, Baylor University; T. Philip Nichols, Baylor University*

Towards a Counter-Propaganda Approach to Democratic Education. *Christopher H. Clark, University of North Dakota; Mardi Schmeichel, University of Nebraska - Lincoln*

Birds Aren’t Real: Vigilante Civic Literacies for Classroom Counterpublics. *William J. Fassbender, Montana State University; Bradley Robinson, Texas State University*

The Messy Problematic of Worldview-Affirming

Misinformation When Trying to Reassemble Democracy.
Cathryn van Kessel, Texas Christian University; Lex Nikola Salazar, Texas Christian University

Chair: *Alexandra Thrall, Baylor University*

Discussant: *Renee Hobbs, University of Rhode Island*

73.056. Cultivating Urban Education Leaders: A Collaborative Mentorship Model for Systemic Transformation. SIG-Mentorship and Mentoring Practices; Symposium
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Los Feliz; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Mentoring: A Collaborative Mentorship Model for Urban Educators and Leaders. *Geleana Drew Alston, North Carolina A&T State University; Stephen D. Hancock, North Carolina A&T State University*

Mentorship Reimagined: The Transformative Impact of Reciprocal Mentoring on Professional Identity in Higher Education. *Tempestt Richardson Adams, Appalachian State University; Derrick Robinson, North Carolina A&T State University; Brian Williams, North Carolina A&T State University; Nakeshia N. Williams, North Carolina A&T State University*

Mentoring in the Storm: Finding Light When Darkness Falls. *Torie Wheatley, Charlotte Mecklenburg Schools; Stephanie Thomas-Woodard, Lenoir-Rhyne University*

Mentorship and Measurable Change: A Personal Journey in a Reciprocal, Research-Driven Model. *Raketa Ouedraogo-Thomas, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Kerri A. Ullucci, Roger Williams University*

Chair: *Chance W. Lewis, University of North Carolina - Charlotte*

Discussant: *Tamera D. Moore, Charleston Southern University*

73.057. Belonging at What Cost? Identifying and Regulating Costs of Existing and Persisting in Educational Spaces. SIG-Motivation in Education; Symposium
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Beaudry B; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

A Qualitative Study on the Costs of Belonging in High School. *Maegan Barbara Arney, Washington University in St. Louis*

Exploring Costs to Belong Among College Students of Color. *Carlton J. Fong, Texas State University; Pedram Zarei, Texas State University*

Belonging Regulation Strategies in High School: Deductive Coding of Student Responses to Low Belonging. *Chris Rozek, Washington University in St. Louis*

Putting Up With It: How College Students Reconcile the Costs of STEM Persistence. *Emily Quinn Rosenzweig, Teachers College, Columbia University; Patrick N. Beymer, University of Cincinnati; Yichi Zhang, University of Georgia; Halle Jacobs, Teachers College, Columbia University; Heather Putman, University of Cincinnati; Kitley Ann Kern, University of Cincinnati*

Chairs: *Chris Rozek, Washington University in St. Louis; Carlton*

J. Fong, Texas State University

Discussant: *Jamaal Matthews, University of Michigan*

73.058. Policy, Teacher Preparation, and (In)Equity in Music Education. SIG-Music Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Georgia II; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Arts Access for All: A Process Evaluation of California's Proposition 28. *Bri'Ann Wright, California State University - Fullerton*

Counting the Cost: Preservice Music Teachers' Degree Financing & Persistence. *Stephanie Prichard, University of Maryland; Kenneth Elpus, University of Maryland*

Cultivating an Equitable Music Teacher Pipeline: An Examination of Student-Teacher Demographic Matching Effects. *David S. Miller, University of Kentucky; David Dockan, Louisiana State University*

Exploring the Motivations of Cooperating Music Teachers in Maryland: A Mixed Methods Study. *Lauren McGinley, University of Maryland; Stacia Pratt, University of Maryland*

Chair: *Jill M Sullivan, Arizona State University*

Discussant: *Karen Salvador, Michigan State University*

73.059. Student engagement in PBL and PjBL learning. SIG-Problem-Based and Project-Based Learning; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Palos Verdes; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Fostering Climate Consciousness Among Elementary Students Through PBL. *Anne E. Martin, Georgia State University*

Beyond Counting Cigarettes: Evaluating Proposition 10 Investments in Early Childhood Problem Solving Skills. *Jianjun Wang, California State University - Bakersfield*

Project-Based Learning in Middle School Science: Curriculum Design, Implementation, and Impacts on Diverse Learners. *Shanna Lillis, Florida Atlantic University; Sabrina F. Sembiante, Florida Atlantic University*

Criticality in Project-Based Learning Classrooms. *Emily E. Virtue, Western Carolina University; Brandi N. Hinnant-Crawford, Clemson University; Liz Bergeron, New Tech Network*

Legitimate Participation in PjBL: Opportunities for Supporting Students Social Bonds Across MLL Levels. *Ella Yonai, University of Georgia; Emily Adah Miller, University of Georgia*

73.060. Responding to the Void: QuantCrit Analyses of Queer and Trans Outcomes across Four Large-Scale Surveys. SIG-Queer Studies; Symposium
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Beaudry A; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

DEI Improves Student Satisfaction: The Impact of Nonbinary BIPOC Student Engagement with DEI. *C. V. Dolan, University of Vermont; Roman Christiaens, Indiana University; Kristopher Oliveira, University of Maryland; Animesh Paul, University of Georgia; Cat Metcalfe, Florida State University; Jason C. Garvey, University of Vermont*

A Multivariate Comparative Analysis of TQ Graduate Student Experiences, Program Perceptions and Health Outcomes. *Kristopher Oliveira, University of Maryland; Animesh Paul, University of Georgia; Roman Christiaens, Indiana University; Cat Metcalfe, Florida State University; C. V. Dolan, University of Vermont; Jason C. Garvey, University of Vermont*

Centering Transfeminine College Students: An Exploration of Transmisogyny Using Large Scale National Data. *Roman Christiaens, Indiana University; Cat Metcalfe, Florida State University; Animesh Paul, University of Georgia; Kristopher Oliveira, University of Maryland; C. V. Dolan, University of Vermont; Jason C. Garvey, University of Vermont*

The Cost of Stress: Mental Health and Dropout Intentions among Queer Graduate Students. *Animesh Paul, University of Georgia; Kristopher Oliveira, University of Maryland; Roman Christiaens, Indiana University; Cat Metcalfe, Florida State University; C. V. Dolan, University of Vermont; Jason C. Garvey, University of Vermont*

Leadership Experiences and Belonging: A Structural Equation Model Across Gender Identity Groups. *Cat Metcalfe, Florida State University; Animesh Paul, University of Georgia; Roman Christiaens, Indiana University; Kristopher Oliveira, University of Maryland; C. V. Dolan, University of Vermont; Jason C. Garvey, University of Vermont*

Chair: *Mario I Suárez, Utah State University*

Discussant: *Amanda J. Davis Simpferfer, College of William & Mary*

73.061. Examining the Intersectionalities of Mathematics and Languages. SIG-Research in Mathematics Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 6; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Co-constructing Fractional Understanding: The Case of Bilingual Children with Identified Learning Disabilities During Problem Solving. *Juanita Maria Silva, Texas State University; IMANEH SOLEIMANI, Texas State University*

Culturally Sustaining Systemic Functional Linguistics Praxis in Mathematics Classrooms for Newly Arrived High School Multilingual Learners. *Seon Ja Chang, University of Georgia; Khanh Bui, University of Georgia; Ruth Harman, University of Georgia*

Revisiting the Register and the Repertoire: Conceptualizing a Mathematics Discourse Rooted in Black Language. *Nickolaus A. Ortiz, Georgia State University; Guilherme Ribeiro, Georgia State University*

We Are the Spanish Teachers, and We Know Mathematics. *Mariana Alvidrez, New Mexico State University; Lidia Herrera-Rocha, EDVantage Analytics LLC; Jennifer Osuna, Stanford University*

Can ChatGPT Help Analyze Collaborative Mathematical Argumentation? Comparing AI Tools for Classroom Argumentation Analysis. *Jennifer Kleiman, University of Georgia; Yizhu Gao, University of Georgia; Xiaoming Zhai, University of Georgia*

Chair: *Melissa A. Gallagher, U.S. Math Recovery Council*

Discussant: *Carlos Nicolas Gómez Marchant, University of Texas at Austin*

73.062. Reimagining School Effectiveness Research: Integrating Context, Culture, and Capacity for Sustainable Change. SIG-School Effectiveness and School Improvement; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum J; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Comparative Analysis of Associations between School-Level Peer Effects and Student Reading Performance Across Asian Countries. *Yeseul Doo, University of Chicago; Baeksan Yu, Gwangju National University of Education*

Fostering School Improvement: Data-Informed Decision-Making in Research-Practice Partnerships. *Linor Lea Hadar, University of Haifa; Haneen Vasel, Beit Berl College*

Searching for stages of effective teaching in pre-primary schools: the contribution of research on play. *Leonidas Kyriakides, University of Cyprus; Victoria Michaelidou, University of Cyprus*

Teacher Collaboration and Student Achievement: A Systematic Review of Empirical Literature. *felipe coloma, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile; Paulo Luis Volante, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile*

Teacher Wait Time – Conditions and Consequences in Contemporary Primary School Classes. *Jasmin Decristan, University of Wuppertal*

Discussant: *SeongGyeong Park, University of Texas at Austin*

73.063. Expanding Research Practice Partnerships: Integrating Youth Voices for Equitable and Impactful Collaboration. SIG-School-University Partnership Research; Structured Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 515B; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

1. Co-designing with Youth to Integrate Systems Thinking and Critical Science Agency in High-School Environmental Engineering (Poster 1). *Yuxi Huang, University of California - Irvine; Taryn M. Williams, University of California - Irvine; Aakriti Bisht, University of California - Irvine; Rossella Santagata, University of California - Irvine; Symone Gyles, University of California - Irvine; Hosun*

Kang, University of California - Irvine; Teresa Hackey, University of California - Irvine; Jennifer J. Long, University of California - Irvine; Sara Ludovise, Orange County Department of Education; Erick Valdez, Orange County Department of Education

2. Youth-Centered Speculative Approaches: Community-Based Data and GIS (Poster 2). *Aakriti Bisht, University of California - Irvine; Teresa Hackey, University of California - Irvine; Rossella Santagata, University of California - Irvine; Hosun Kang, University of California - Irvine; Symone Gyles, University of California - Irvine; Yuxi Huang, University of California - Irvine; Taryn M. Williams, University of California - Irvine; Jennifer J. Long, University of California - Irvine; Sara Ludovise, Orange County Department of Education; Erick Valdez, Orange County Department of Education*
3. A Youth-led Research Collaborative to Improve Student Mental Health in a Midwestern Urban Community (Poster 3). *Bianca Burch, Wayne State University; Erica B. Edwards, Wayne State University; Imani Foster, 482 Forward*
4. Co-designing for Climate Justice in Middle School STEM (Poster 4). *Angela Calabrese, University of Michigan; Wisam Sedawi, University of Michigan; Batoul Abdallah, University of Michigan*
5. Youth Voice and School Mental Health: Identifying Facilitators and Barriers to Participation (Poster 5). *Katie Eklund, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Sinéad O'Neill, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Kierin Barnett, University of Wisconsin - Madison*
6. Co-designing Tools for Community Climate Action: Participatory and Culturally Sustaining Research, Education, and Organizing (Poster 6). *Victoria Nguyen, University of California - Irvine; Erika Mayoral-Ramirez, GREEN-MPNA; Leonel Flores, GREEN-MPNA; Aylin Camacho, GREEN-MPNA; Marianna Davison, University of California - Irvine; Tatiana Flores, University of California - Irvine; Victoria Lowerson Bredow, University of California - Irvine*
7. Partnering with Youth to Reimagine Math Engagement: How a Research-Practice Team Co-Designed Solutions to Improve Equity (Poster 7). *Samantha E. Holquist, Child Trends; Ta-yang Hsieh, Search Institute; Alyssa Scott, Child Trends; Marisa K. Crowder, The ElevatEd Initiative; Mark Vincent B. Yu, NA; Claire Kelley, Child Trends; Olivia Reyes, Child Trends*
8. Troubling Safety: A Youth Participatory Action Research Project by the Youth Research Council (Poster 8). *Meagan Call-Cummings, Johns Hopkins University; Bethany Monea, University of the District of Columbia*

Chairs: *Yuxi Huang, University of California - Irvine; Aakriti Bisht, University of California - Irvine*

Discussant: *Symone Gyles, University of California - Irvine*

73.064. Defining Accessible Social and Emotional Learning for

Students with Learning Differences. SIG-Social and Emotional Learning; Symposium
Westin Bonaventure, Level 3, Santa Monica B; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

A Barrier Analysis of Tier 1 SEL Programming in the United States. *Christina Cipriano, Yale University; Michael McCarthy, Yale Child Study Center; Gabrielle Rappolt-Schlichtmann, EdTogether, Inc.; Melissa Stoffers, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Cheyeon Ha, Yale University*
Educator Validation of Barriers to Social and Emotional Learning. *Michael McCarthy, Yale Child Study Center; Melissa Stoffers, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Cheyeon Ha, Yale University; Gabrielle Rappolt-Schlichtmann, EdTogether, Inc.; Christina Cipriano, Yale University*
Student Validation of Barriers to and Solutions for SEL. *Melissa Stoffers, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Michael McCarthy, Yale Child Study Center; Cheyeon Ha, Yale University; Gabrielle Rappolt-Schlichtmann, EdTogether, Inc.; Christina Cipriano, Yale University*

Chair: *Christina Cipriano, Yale University*

Discussant: *Kimberly A. Schonert-Reichl, University of Illinois at Chicago*

73.065. And some will speak... SIG-Social Studies Research; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum H; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Conceiving Reproductive Justice in Social Studies Education. *Rebecca Cooper Geller, University of Georgia*
"I Hate Slavery, Too": A Linguistic Analysis of PragerU's Leo and Layla Series. *Edgar Díaz, Utah State University; Matt DeRoo, Florida International University; Kate Arnold*
Narrowed Paths?: Teacher Perceptions of How Presidential Elections Fit into Their Curriculum. *Erin A. Bronstein, University of Michigan - Dearborn*
"Some Things Were Tiptoeed Around": Black Elementary Preservice Teachers' on Historic Plantation Sites. *Kristen Duncan, Clemson University*
Teaching History Without Roots: Analyzing One Social Studies Teacher's Choices in a Rural Conservative Context. *Al Wood, Michigan State University*

Chair: *Brandon J. Beck, University of Maryland Baltimore County*

Discussant: *Wayne Journell, University of North Carolina - Greensboro*

73.066. Unforgetting Patriarchy in Mathematics Education Research. SIG-Socio-Political Issues in Mathematics and Science Education; Symposium

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum A; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

When Girl is Not the Problem and Gender Analysis is Not the

Only Solution. *Tesha Sengupta-Irving, University of California - Berkeley; Josephine Ingram, University of California - Berkeley*

Contando Historias Matemáticas: Making Visible the Complexity of Mathematical Master Narratives in Storytelling. *Sandra Zuniga, San José State University*
(Re)membering Black Girls' Mathematical Brilliance: The Patriarchal Politics of Advanced Math Access. *Shanyce L. Campbell, University of Pittsburgh*

Quick and Languid: Shifting Tempos in the Learning of Mathematics. *Arundhati Velamuri, New York University*

Chair: *Catherine C. Riegle-Crumb, University of Notre Dame*

Discussants: *Maisie L. Gholson, University of Michigan; Melissa Sommerfeld Gresalfi, Vanderbilt University*

73.067. Anti-Racist Critical Perspectives Diversifying Special Education Research: Challenging Traditional Narratives of Objectivity, Neutrality, and Science. SIG-Special and Inclusive Education Research; Symposium

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 3; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Critical Historiography of Special Education Research and Praxis: Advancing Collective Race and Dis/Ability Positionings. *Mildred Boveda, Pennsylvania State University; David I. Hernandez-Saca, University of Northern Iowa; Catherine Kramarczuk Voulgarides, Hunter College - CUNY*

The Numbers and the Narrative: A Critical Mixed Methods Synthesis of Disproportionality Literature Across Paradigms. *Rebecca A. Cruz, Johns Hopkins University; Allison Firestone, San Francisco Unified School District; Sarah A. Caroleo, Brown University; Rachel Saperstein McClam, Johns Hopkins University; Isun Malekghassemi, Johns Hopkins University; Logan McDermott, Johns Hopkins University; Claire Shin, Johns Hopkins University; Abigail Howes, Johns Hopkins University; Hailey Love, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Unchilding & Purposeful Remembering: Education in the Carceral State. *Candice Jeehae Kim, Stanford University; Subini Ancy Annamma, Stanford University; Michael O'Key, Stanford University; Anmol Gupta, Stanford University; Greg Prieto, University of San Diego*

A Mother-Son Dialogue on Anti-Blackness, Racism, Ableism, Special Education, and the Dangling Carrot of Giftedness. *Elijah Stoutenburg, Pennsylvania State University; Lydia L. Ocasio-Stoutenburg, Pennsylvania State University*

Countering Ableism and Racism in Mathematics and Special Education Contexts: Exploring Possibilities through Maroon Knowledges. *Paulo Tan, University of California - Santa Cruz; Rachel Lambert, University of California - Santa Barbara; Alexis Padilla, Independent Scholar*

Chair: *David J. Connor, Hunter College - CUNY*

Discussant: *Nicholas S. Bell, University of Connecticut*

73.068. Centering Liberatory Health Equity Lenses in Interdisciplinary Approaches to the Promotion of Youth Well-Being. SIG-Stress, Coping, and Resilience; Symposium

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 301B; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Centering Black Youth, Rewriting the System: Toward Equitable School Mental Health Futures. *Shlon A. Smith, Stepping Stone Therapy*

Examining a Pedagogical Strategy for Engaging Youth in Participatory Health Equity Research. *Kate Somerville, University of Wisconsin-Madison*

Supporting Undocumented Youth Wellbeing through a Culturally Adapted Online Intervention. *Jose Manuel Gonzalez Vera, Stanford University; Melanie Domenech Rodriguez, Utah State University; Alejandro Vázquez, University of Tennessee; Guadalupe San Miguel, Utah State University; Korena Klimczak, Utah State University; Miriam Mukasa, Utah State University; Damilola Daramola, Utah State University; Michael Levin, Utah State University; Jenifer Garcia Mendoza, El Puente de Encuentros*

Centering Children Through Economic Policy: Attitudes Toward Guaranteed Income for Families. *Monica De La Cruz, University of California - Berkeley*

Chair: *Kate Somerville, University of Wisconsin-Madison*

Discussant: *Jessika Bottiani, University of Virginia*

73.069. Advancing Mixture Modeling Methodology: Model Specification, Class Enumeration, and Measurement Invariance for Complex Data Structures. SIG-Structural Equation Modeling and Multilevel Modeling Methods; Symposium

InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Echo Park; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Unmodeled DIF in Latent Class Analysis: Consequences for Class Enumeration. *Dina Naji Arch, University of California - Santa Barbara; Karen L. Nylund-Gibson, University of California - Santa Barbara*

Investigating the Impacts of Longitudinal Measurement Non-Invariance in Latent Transition Analysis. *Boshi Wang, Georgia State University; Katherine E. Masyn, Georgia State University*

When Is RI-LTA Necessary? A Monte Carlo Comparison of Latent Transition Models. *Delwin Carter, University of California - Santa Barbara; Karen L. Nylund-Gibson, University of California - Santa Barbara*

The Role of Class Separation in Class Enumeration for Latent Profile Analysis with Nested Data. *Angela D. Starrett, University of South Carolina; Katherine E. Masyn, Georgia State University*

Developing a Bayesian Cross-Classified Growth Mixture

Model to Account for Student Mobility. *Audrey J. Leroux, Georgia Institute of Technology; Tonghui Xu, University of Houston; Yan Wang, University of Massachusetts Lowell*
Chair: *Katherine E. Masyn, Georgia State University*
Discussant: *Tiffany A. Whittaker, University of Texas at Austin*

Division and SIG Roundtables

73.070. AERA Roundtable Session Saturday 9:45 am;
Roundtable Session

73.070-1. Educators' Critical Reflections on Curriculum Questions (Table 1). Division B - Curriculum Studies; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Curriculum Theory: The Importance of Ethical Curriculum Development. *Nelofar Khamisani, Kansas State University*
Hermanas Escritoras [Sister Writers]: Negotiating Our Science Writer Identities as Chicana/Latinas in STEM. *Anna Carolina Peñaloza, University of California - Davis; Camille Anne Korb, University of California - Davis; Eimy Nino Barrera, University of California - Davis; Ashley Garcia, University of California - Davis; Aylin Andrade, University of California - Davis*

Privileged Plates: A Registered Dietitian-Educator's Curriere Inquiry in a Time of Crisis. *Rachel Villarreal, University of Texas Rio Grande Valley*

The Conceptualizations and Enactments of Culturally-Informed Pedagogies among Higher Education Biology Instructors. *Angelita Rivera, Stanford University; Shima Salehi, Stanford University*

Chair: *Uma Maheshwari Ganesan, University of Texas - Rio Grande Valley*

73.070-2. Theoretical Analyses of Learning Environments (Table 2). Division B - Curriculum Studies; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Analyzing Emotions and Affect in the Curriculum: A Critical Discourse Analysis. *Brittany Jones, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

Confining Curiosity: Whiteness as Property in a Behavior-Focused Science Classroom. *Maizie Dyess, University of Rhode Island*

Folding Migration: Affect, Subjectivation, and Informal Learning at the Museum of Chinese in America. *William Zhou, The George Washington University*

Chair: *Danielle Charlemagne, University of Georgia*

73.070-3. Speculative Fiction, Expansive Literacies, and Futurities (Table 3). Division B - Curriculum Studies; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

“Won’t You Accompany Me”: Friction, Contact Zones, and Accompaniment Curriculum. *Thomas Albright, Georgia State University*

The Audacity of Speculative Teaching. *Hilary Naa-Afi Tackie, SUNY - College at New Paltz*

Queer love in the archive (the case of Casimir Carter): Materializing familial forgetting. *David Lewkowich, University of Alberta*

Bewildering Writing Practices: Speculative Fiction and Affective Possibilities. *Bradley Sullivan, University of Oregon*

73.070-4. Problematizing the Evidence Base (Table 4). Division B - Curriculum Studies; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Embodying Democracy in K–12 Classrooms: Wayfinding Through Rich and Rough Curricular Terrain. *Kyle Hamilton, University of British Columbia - Okanagan; Margaret A. Macintyre Latta, University of British Columbia - Okanagan*

Unforgetting Disability: How Three School Districts Enact Pennsylvania’s Disability-Inclusive Curriculum Policy. *Christa S. Bialka, Villanova University; Nicole Hansen, Seton Hall University; Irene P. Kan, Villanova University; St. Rachel Elora Ustanny, Seton Hall University; Taylor Marin, Villanova University; Evelyn Sperry, Villanova University; Timothy Krushinski, Pennsylvania Department of Education; Nichole Kopco, Pennsylvania Training and Technical Assistance Network*

What’s Missing Matters: A Null Curriculum Analysis of Secondary ELA Programs and Adolescent Reading Needs Post NAEP 2024. *Chae D’Ann Ray, The University of Texas Rio Grande Valley*

When “Research-Based” Isn’t Enough: Developmental Underpinnings and the Matter of Interpretation. *Laronnda V. Thompson, University of Pennsylvania*

73.070-5. Past and future of (material not just symbolic) decoloniality in curriculum (Table 5). Division B - Curriculum Studies; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Content Analysis of African History Before 1492 CE in World and Black History State Standards. *Clarence Ball, Fordham University*

Sonic Memory and the Curriculum of Refusal: Black Educational Hauntings and Futurity. *Ja'Corie A. Maxwell, University of Oklahoma*

Speculative Frameworks for Liberation: Designing Afrofuturist Biology to Reclaim Legacy and Envision Futures. *Michele Williams, University of Illinois at Chicago; Isaiah M. Stewart, University of Illinois at Chicago; Autumn Rouse, University of Illinois at Chicago; Lucienne Petit, University of Illinois Chicago; Terrell R Morton, University of Illinois at Chicago*

The Roots of Tomorrow: A Framework for an Agrarian Resilience Curriculum. *Ayu Fitriani, Universitas Nusa Cendana; Muhammad Hilal Sudarbi, University of Groningen*

We Imagined Otherwise: Black Speculative Pedagogy as Futuring Praxis in STEM Education. *Earl E Lee, Arizona State University*

73.070-6. Exploring Marginalized Identities and Liberatory Frameworks for Justice in Teaching, Learning, and Workforce Policies (Table 6). Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Choice as Control: The Ideological Work of Georgia's Voucher Discourse. *Jennifer Glisson, Texas Tech University; Ronald Orr, Regents School of Charlottesville; Robert J. Lynn, Texas Tech University; Joshua M. Cruz, Texas Tech University*

Learn to Earn: Job Corps, Educational Training, and the Racialization of the 1960s War on Poverty. *Kenzo K. Sung, Loyola Marymount University*

The Stories We Receive: Utilizing Master and Alternative Narratives in Transgender Policy Analysis. *Alexandria B Gribble, Florida Atlantic University; Erica Simpson, Colorado State University; Meagan S. Richard, Old Dominion University*

Triaging the Last Public Good: In Dialogue With Du Bois, Washington, and Freire. *Efrain Brito, California Polytechnic State University - San Luis Obispo; Xavier J. Monroe, AAAS Fellow @ National Science Foundation; Anthony Muro Villa, University of California - Riverside*

Unforgetting Black Teacher Histories, Imagining Liberatory Futures: Race, Class, and Resistance in Neoliberal NYC. *Jasmine Hawkins-White, New York University*

Discussant: *Kenzo K. Sung, Loyola Marymount University*

73.070-7. From Access to Transformation: Disability, Giftedness, Music, and Neurodivergence in Education (Table 7). Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Mapping the Optics of Predatory Inclusion in Gifted Education: Converging and Diverging Perspectives of Leaders. *Brittany Nicole Anderson, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Allison Roda, Molloy University*

Policy, Perception, and Practice: Music Education in High-Need Contexts Under Connecticut's Accountability System. *Juliana George, Teachers College, Columbia University; Drew Xavier Coles, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Remediating Transition Challenges: Disability Accommodations from K-12 to College. *Allison Comeaux, University of Louisiana at Lafayette; Amanda S. Mayeaux, University of Louisiana at Lafayette*

We See What's NExT: Why Building Transformative Participatory Research Approaches for Neurodivergent Stakeholders Matters. *Janelle A. Johnson, North Carolina State University*

Chair: *Antonio L. Ellis, American University*

Discussant: *Janelle A. Johnson, North Carolina State University*

73.070-8. Families as Social Context (Table 8). Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Between Words and Worlds: How Discourse Shapes a Trans Woman's Evolving Identity and Familial Experience. *Keith Anthony Griffin, University of Colorado - Boulder; Melissa Braaten, University of Colorado - Boulder*

Families Engaging Their Knowledges and Epistemologies in Service of Community. *Elizabeth Gil, Fordham University; Nimo Abdi, The Ohio State University*

Naming Whiteness: Racial Identity in Family, School, and Peer Contexts. *Piljoo P. Kang, Seattle Pacific University; Mia Erickson, Seattle Pacific University*

"Navigating Early Motherhood in Hawai'i": Korean American Mothers' Early Parenting Experiences. *Shin Ae Han, University of Hawai'i at Manoa*

Chair: *Gabriela López, Stanford University*

73.070-9. Governing the Modern School District: Data, AI, and the Impact of Local Economics (Table 9). SIG-Districts in Research & Reform; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Do Rising House Values Lift Scores? A Ten-Year Within-Municipality Analysis. *Baeksan Yu, Gwangju National University of Education; Hyejung Lim, Korea University; Hyevin Shin, University of Florida*

How Are School Districts in California Responding to ChatGPT? A Policy Analysis of Five K-12 Guidelines. *Shiyang Zhang, University of Pennsylvania; Xianghui Meng, Columbia University*

Local Governance and Digital Platforms: Explaining the Variation in School Boards' Data-Accessibility Tools. *Ghadir Al Saghir, Pennsylvania State University*

Chair: *Amanda U. Potterton, University of Kentucky*

73.070-10. Reimagining Leadership Preparation (Table 10).

SIG-Learning and Teaching in Educational Leadership; Roundtable Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Centering Identity and Multilingualism in Educational Leadership Preparation Programs. *Elisabeth Kim, Lehman College; Kalah Larison Ishimaru, California State University - Monterey Bay*

Principal and HR Administrator Perspectives on Determining First-Time Assistant Principal "Fit": Implications for University Preparation Programs. *Kimberly Jamison, University of North Carolina - Wilmington; Helen Gross, Onslow County Schools*

Principal Readiness: A Comparative Case Study of Alumni Preparedness After Completing a Principal Preparation Program. *LaMonica Williams, Purdue University; Marlon I Cummings, Governors State University*

Reimagining Principal Preparation: Enhancing Learning and Teaching Through an Open Educational Resource: Texas Public School Law. *Cynthia Angélica Gallardo, Texas A&M International University*

Chair: *Nahed Abdelrahman, The University of Southern Mississippi*

73.071. AERA Roundtable Session Saturday 9:45 am - Gold 1; Roundtable Session

73.071-1. Educating Futures: Culture, Code, and Creativity in Transformative Pedagogies (Table 1). Division K -

Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Arts-in-a-Box, Futures-in-e-Making: Reimagining Online Arts Teacher Education for Sustainability and Social Engagement. *Victoria Pavlou, Frederick University*

From Gesture to Meaning: Cultivating Musicality Through Culturally Sustaining Erhu Pedagogy in Higher Education. *WEN LI, Newcastle University*

Plays and Scripts: How Integrating Computational Thinking into Literacy Lessons Promotes Student and Professional Learning. *Robert Macias, Northern Arizona University; Samuel Severance, Northern Arizona University*

Sensing the Algorithm: A Multisensory Dialogic Pedagogy for AI-Integrated Art Education. *Jiayi Guo, University of Georgia; Hsin Fang, Florida State University*

Chair: *Victoria Pavlou, Frederick University*

Discussant: *Anastasia L. Betts, Learnology Labs*

73.071-2. Lead Where You Are: Collaboration and Pedagogical Innovation in Context (Table 2). Division K -

Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Agency and Accountability: How Professional Relationships Shape Teacher Agency. *Christopher Carter, University of Kansas*

Discipline Dilemmas: How Memphis Charter School Teachers Navigate Culturally Responsive Practices Amid Exclusionary Policies. *Emily Hannah McFarland, Baylor University; Anne J. Stekete, Baylor University*

Teachers' Well-Being and Innovative Behavior: A Moderated Mediation Model of Insider Status and Authentic Leadership. *Zeqing Xu, East China Normal University*

Teacher Agency in School-Based Youth Participatory Action Research. *Kampanart Chaiyarat, Teachers College, Columbia University; Noa Ovadia, Teachers College, Columbia University; Beth C. Rubin, Teachers College, Columbia University; Maya Berrol-Young, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Reclaiming Teacher Agency through Teranga: A Culturally Grounded Participatory Action Research Study in Senegal. *Oumar Moussa Djigo, Michigan State University*

73.071-3. Honoring Disability As Identity: Teaching and Teacher Education for Inclusion (Table 3). Division K -

Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

ADHD and Inclusive Teaching: Exploring Knowledge, Self-Efficacy, and Embodied Educational Practices in Italy. *Anna Maria Mariani, Università Telematica Pegaso; Eugenia Treglia, Università Telematica Pegaso*

Infusing Disability Justice in General Education Teacher Preparation Settings: An Imperative for Inclusion. *Maria Mavrides Calderon, Hunter College - CUNY; Isabel Mavrides-Calderon, Barnard College*

Sustaining Teacher Candidates with Disabilities: A Call to Action Across All Teacher Preparation Programs. *Jolan Smith, California State University - Long Beach*

Chair: *Emilee A Baker, University of Minnesota*

Discussant: *Emilee A Baker, University of Minnesota*

73.071-4. Developing Intentionality Among Pre-service STEM Teachers (Table 4). Division K -

Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Influence of Teacher Observer Content and Pedagogical Knowledge on Their Content-Focused Observations and Feedback Quality. *Elizabeth R Goldberg, Texas Tech University; Jian Wang, Texas Tech University*

Learning to Listen with Curiosity and Generosity: New Approaches to Science and Math Interviews. *Mallika Scott, California State University - Fullerton; Kathryn Lanouette, William & Mary*

Sources of Preservice Elementary Teachers' Integrated STEM Teaching Self-efficacy: A Multi-institutional Study. *Deepika Menon, University of Nebraska - Lincoln; Jeanna R. Wieselmann, Southern Methodist University; Grace*

Morison, Southern Methodist University; Sarah A. Haines, Towson University; Sumreen Asim, Indiana University - Southeast; Allison Johnson, University of Nebraska - Lincoln
Influences of Elementary Science Preservice Teachers' Content Understanding on Their Use of Pedagogical Content Knowledge. *Yanhong Moore, McGregor Independent School District; Jian Wang, Texas Tech University*

I Love You: Centering Critical Love to Disrupt Oppression in Teacher Education. *Kristen Schaffer, Mount Royal University; Daniela Quintero, Mount Royal University; Kodie Rollan, Chromatic Theatre; Reggie San Jose, Mount Royal University*

Chair: *Kelly Davis, University of Houston*

73.071-5. The Education of Justice-Oriented Teacher Educators (Table 5). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Constructing a Migration-centered Approach to Teacher Preparation: Revisiting Ethnographic Puzzles from Dialogues with Immigrant Youth. *Brian Tauzel, Western Washington University; Saraswati Noel, Western Washington University; Elizabeth E. Schuster, University of Washington*

Lessons in Contradictions: Reinforcing Equity and Justice-oriented Teacher Dispositions in the Trump Era. *Terry Stockton, Grand Valley State University; Sarah Chase, Grand Valley State University*

Navigating Challenges, Naming Supports in Teacher Education: A Case Study of Justice-Oriented Instructors. *Cheetara A Hudson, Loyola University Chicago*

It's Personal and Professional: A Reflection on Supporting Teachers in Baltimore City. *Paul Koh, Towson University; Stephanie Mojibola, Baltimore City Public Schools*

Reflective Praxis for Collective Liberation: Teacher Educator Inquiry Toward Justice. *Ayesha Rabadi-Raol, Sonoma State University; Lisel A. Murdock-Perriera, Sonoma State University*

Chair: *Tamara Handy, Teachers College, Columbia University*

73.071-6. Disrupting Neutrality, Designing Justice: Minority-Serving and Antiracist Innovations in Teacher Preparation (Table 6). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

From Theory to Empowerment: Advancing HBCU Teacher Preparation through Integrative Literacy Theory. *Cheron Hunter Davis, Florida A&M University*

"Sitting With" the Past to Move Into the Future: Aufarbeitung as Disruptive Force in Teacher Education. *Jocelyn A. Glazier, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Taylor William Schmidt, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Abigail Paquin, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Anja Wilken, University of Hamburg; Andreas Bonnet, University of Hamburg*

Supporting Pre-service Teachers in Critical and Antiracist Teaching: Complexities and Contradictions about Neutrality. *Noah Jefferson, Westfield State University; Juliet Lee, Westfield State University*

Utilization of Minority-Serving Status in Teacher Preparation Programs: Towards a Framework for Minority-Serving Programs. *Lillie Ko-Wong, University of California - San Diego*

Weaving Equity and Artificial Intelligence in Preservice Teacher Education: One Assignment Across Four Courses. *Ardavan Eizadirad, Wilfrid Laurier University; Keri Ewart, Wilfrid Laurier University; Ryan Neepin, Wilfrid Laurier University; Steve Sider, Wilfrid Laurier University*

Chair: *Hengyi Liu, University of Southern Indiana*

73.071-7. Policy in Action: Professional Learning, Coaching Models, and Equity Commitments (Table 7). Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Contested Commitments: A Content Analysis of Equity Policies Framing Leadership Diversity Goals Despite Backlash. *Kimberly Clarida, Michigan State University; Kait Ogden, University of Texas at Austin; Ja'Miya Grace, Michigan State University*

Staffing Matters: Comparing Coach Staffing Models and Their Influence on Coaching Practice. *Angela Marie Hardy, Digital Promise; Lauren H. McMahon, Digital Promise Global; Nicola Hodkowsky, Digital Promise Global; Mai Chou Vang, Digital Promise*

Symbolic Reform, Radical Hopes: A Critical Look at NYC's Implicit Bias Training Rollout. *Abby C. Emerson, Touro University*

The Impact of Teacher Professional Learning Designed to Support Effective Use of High-Quality Instructional Materials. *Andrew J. Wayne, American Institutes for*

Research; Sami Kitmitto, American Institutes for Research; ChenYu Hung, American Institutes for Research; Cheryl Graczewski, American Institutes for Research
Chair: *Jawanza Kalonji Rand, Teachers College, Columbia University*

73.071-8. Young People's Perceptions of Civic and Political Engagement (Table 8). SIG-Democratic Citizenship in Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

From Protest to Policy: How Gen-Z Activists Build Power Across Boundaries. *Tara Lynn Bartlett, Arizona State University*

Is It Critical Social Analysis? Conservative and Liberal Youth Social Media Posts During an Election. *Sara Wilf, California Polytechnic State University; Samantha Quiroz, California State Polytechnic University - Pomona; Kendall Reed, Bates College; Elena Maker Castro, University of California - Los Angeles*

"You think big originally": Exploring student perceptions of civic engagement within a civic action curriculum. *Joshua Littenberg-Tobias, GBH; Rob Martinelle, Boston University; Kaylene Mae Stevens, Boston University; Kensy Jordan, GBH*

Chair: *Halleli Pinson, Ben Gurion University of the Negev*

73.071-9. Play and Learning (Table 9). SIG-Early Education and Child Development; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Exploring the Social Architecture of Peer Engagement in Preschool Classrooms: A Social Network Analysis. *Taehee Kim, University of Georgia; Mihyun Kim, University of Georgia; Kristen L Bub, University of Georgia*

Let Them Play: A Social-Emotional Play Intervention to Negate Adverse Behaviors of Kindergarten Students. *Kyler P. Leiter, Mount Saint Mary's University; Molly S. Dunn, Notre Dame of Maryland University*

Killing Elsa and bubble parties: Enduring lessons about navigating crisis through play. *Minsun Shin, Montclair State University; Victoria I. Puig, Montclair State University*

Symbolic Interaction Theory-Based Spatial Language and Action Representation of Young Children During Block Play. *xiaoli Yang, The Open University of Sichuan*

Distinctive Pictures of Practice in a Play-Based Prekindergarten Program. *Kristin L. Whyte, DePaul University*

Chair: *Minsun Shin, Montclair State University*

73.072. AERA Roundtable Session Saturday 9:45 am - Gold 2;
Roundtable Session

73.072-1. Teacher Education and Professional Development (Table 1). SIG-Early Education and Child Development; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

[Reading Application]TM supports Achievement of Early Literacy Skills among students with IEPs. *Amanda Siebert-Evenstone, Age of Learning; Eric H. Setoguchi, Age of Learning, Inc.; Hee Jin Bang, Age of Learning*

Examining Preschool Teacher Nutrition Teaching Efficacy and Practice Changes: A Mixed Methods Case Study. *Eleanor Churchland, MetriKs; Casey E Hanna, Binghamton University - SUNY; Toni A. May, Binghamton University - SUNY; Kathleen Provinzano, Binghamton University - SUNY; Kristin L.K. Koskey, Drexel University*

A Case Study Examining Second Grade Teachers and Their Students in Texas Sensemaking of Instruction. *Christopher P. Brown, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Lauren C. McKenzie, University of Texas at Austin*

Preschool Teachers' Application of Scaffolding Strategies that Support Extensions in Children's Mathematics Learning. *Fei Xu, Oakland University; Tomoko Wakabayashi, Oakland University; Jill Claxton, HighScope Educational Research Foundation*

What Drives Professional Fulfillment for Early Childhood Educators of Color? Workplace Relationships Are the Key. *Xiangyu Zhao, University of Virginia; Lieny Jeon, University of Virginia*

Chair: *Christopher P. Brown, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

73.072-2. Translanguaging Myths in World Language Education: What's the Real Story and the Future? (Table 2). SIG-Second Language Research; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Translanguaging Myths Deconstructed and Reconstructed. *Nicole King, University of Rhode Island; Zhongfeng Tian, Rutgers University - Newark*

Translanguaging in a culturally and linguistically diverse Mandarin FLES program. *Xinyue Lu, Howard University; Zhongfeng Tian, Rutgers University - Newark*

"Context matters!": A cross-national comparative study on world language teachers' perceptions and practices of translanguaging. *Ying Xiong, Pennsylvania State University*
(Trans)bordering as Pedagogy in World Language Education. *Gengqi Xiao, University of Wisconsin-Madison; L.J. Randolph, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Chairs: *Nicole King, University of Rhode Island; Zhongfeng Tian, Rutgers University - Newark*

Discussant: *Li Wei, UCL Institute of Education*

73.072-3. Elevating Practitioner Voices (Table 3). SIG-Teacher as Researcher; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

An Instructional Architecture for Promoting Productive STEM Identity in Underrepresented Minoritized Secondary Mathematics Students. *Michele Mahady Haberlach, Washington State University - Vancouver*

Let the Children Lead: A Teacher Action Research Study on Student Agency and Values as Curriculum. *Margo Brooke Pellmar, Gideon Hausner Jewish Day School; Allison JoAnn Lester, Arizona State University*

Of Discourse and Demerits: One Teacher's Experience Implementing Discourse Moves in an Urban Post-COVID Classroom. *Kanushri Wadhwa, Phoenix Charter Academy*

Writing Out Loud: Investigating the Impact of Dialogic Conversation on Students' Writing Agency and Identity. *Kristen Walsh, Northern Illinois University; Kenneth Lakowski, Northern Illinois University*

Chair: *Mary Klehr, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

73.072-4. Critical Friendships and Collaboration: Self-Study Journeys of Friendship, Dialogue, and Resistance (Table 4). SIG-Self-Study of Teacher Education Practices; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Growing Through Friendship: A Co/Autoethnographic Self-Study of Two Women Scholars in. *Donna Volpe, Ramsey Board of Education; Shanna Dawn Anderson, Montclair State University*

Mindful resistance: Utilizing textual critical friends to (re)establish our footings amid a polycrisis. *Laura C. Haniford, University of New Mexico; Laurie A. Ramirez, Appalachian State University; Valerie A. Allison, Susquehanna University*

Norms, and Roles, and Personalities, Oh My!: Our Journey as Best Friends into Critical Friendship. *Katie Brkich, Georgia Southern University; Kristen L Shumbera, Texas A&M University*

Success in the Shadow: Critical Duoethnography of Learning, Refusal, and Resistance. *Charlton Long, Arizona State University; Tipsuda Chaomuangkhong, Arizona State University*

Chair: *Brandon M. Butler, Old Dominion University*

73.072-5. The Impact of Policy and Politics in Education (Table 5). SIG-Politics of Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Changing the Course: Coalitions, Educational Reforms and Shadow Policymaking in Education in India. *Anurag Shukla, Indian Institute of Management Ahmedabad; Aishwarya Sharma, National Institute of Educational Planning and Administration*

The Ecology of US Education Nonprofits. *Jose Eos Trinidad, University of California - Berkeley*

Chair: *Arturo Rodriguez, Boise State University*

73.072-6. Navigating Identity, Culture and Heritage Languages in Diverse Contexts (Table 6). SIG-Bilingual Education Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

"I feel most authentic teaching in Hmong": Hmong heritage speakers' experiences as heritage language teachers. *Lee Her, Lehigh University*

(Re)membering and (Re)imagining: A Collective Autoethnography of Transnational MotherScholars Raising Bi/Multilingual Children. *Mariana Lima Becker, University of Georgia; Xiaochen Du, Independent Scholar; Kooun Park, University of Hawai'i - West O'ahu; Tairan Qiu, Stanford University*

Against Erasure: Indigenous Sites of Possibility in Multilingual Practices across the Maya Diaspora Yucatan-California. *Patricia Baquedano-Lopez, University of California - Berkeley*

Bilanguaging Love as Resistance Praxis in Brazilian Transnational Families in the United States. *Rosangela Araujo Silva, University of Georgia; Mariana Lima Becker, University of Georgia*

Bilingual Identity and Emotional Expression: Language Preferences of Arab Teachers in Jewish Schools. *Eman Abo-Zaed Arar, Texas State University*

73.072-7. Paso a paso early experiences with language, literacy and identity. (Table 7). SIG-Bilingual Education Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

English Language and Social-Emotional Skills of Dual Language Learners: Understanding the Role of Linguistic Environments. *Jun Wang, The Ohio State University; Rachel Hur, Johns Hopkins University; Lieny Jeon, University of Virginia*

Latina Immigrant Mother Perspectives from a Parent Literacy Class at a Bilingual Dual-Language Elementary School. *Reena Valvani, San Leandro Unified School District; Cati V. de los Rios, University of California - Berkeley; Sindy Quiroa, San Leandro Unified School District; Dinora Cibrian Soto, San Leandro Unified School District; Kelly Anabella Tellez Ortega, San Leandro School District*

Head Start and Early Head Start Teachers' Beliefs About Bilingualism: A Convergent Mixed Methods Study. *Jisun Rachel Oh, University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign; Marie Wagner, Rockhurst University*

Exploring School Readiness Profiles at Kindergarten Entry Among Latine Dual Language Learners. *Monica Romero, University of Texas at Austin; Mariana Davila, University of Texas at Austin; Daisy Barrientos, University of Texas at Austin*

Teaching for Equity: Translanguaging as a Transformative Practice in Early Childhood Language Education. *Lijuan Shi, Bard High School Early College; Jiaxuan Zong, University of Maryland*

73.072-8. Systemic Access, Lived Experiences: Pursuing Authentic Inclusion in Postsecondary Education (Table 8). SIG-Disability Studies in Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Disability Justice Dreams and Loving Corrections of IPSE. *Sara Jo Soldovieri, The IDEAL School; Teukie Martin, Syracuse University; Nikkia D. Borowski, Syracuse University*

Exploring Autism Support Programs in U.S. Postsecondary Education: Practices, Decision-Making, and Perceived Effectiveness. *Angela Barbour, University of Oklahoma*

Reimagining Postsecondary Inclusion: Emergency Preparedness Planning for Students with Intellectual Disabilities in Higher Education. *Allie J. Boquet, Louisiana State University; Paul Mooney, Louisiana State University*

The Experiences of Queer and Trans Students with Intellectual Disability within Inclusive Post Secondary Education. *Morgan Jacobs, Syracuse University; Beth Myers, Syracuse University*

Witnessing the Ableist Campus. *Katie E. Ducett, SUNY - College at Cortland*

Chair: *Vandana Sharma, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

73.072-9. Unforgetting Bias and Reimagining Systems: Novel Mixed Methods Approaches for Educational Equity and Decision-Making (Table 9). Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Reimagining Equity in a Borderland District: Lessons from a Comprehensive Equity Assessment. *Katarzyna Razynska, MAEC; Kelly Ocasio, University of Texas at Austin; Miranda Best, Mid Atlantic Equity Consortium; Karmen Roulard, MAEC*

Unforgetting Bias through a Neuroscience-Informed Mixed-Methods Critical Consciousness Training (CCT) for Special Education Decision-Making. *Faith Olivia Lynn*

Garrington, University of Minnesota; LeAnne Johnson, University of Minnesota; Philip Da Zelazo, University of Minnesota

The Impact of Teacher Performance Pay Programs on Student Academic Achievement: A Meta-Analytic Review. *Ran Zhao, Beijing Normal University; YUHONG DU, Beijing Normal University*

Chair: *Krisanna L. Machtmes, Ohio University*

73.073. AERA Roundtable Session Saturday 9:45 am - Gold 3;
Roundtable Session

73.073-1. Case Studies of Large Scale Data Systems: Modeling Best Practices (Table 1). SIG-Advanced Studies of National Databases; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Decoding Tragedy: A Historic Quantitative Ethnographic Analysis of Pilot Discourse Before Aviation Accidents. *Abdulla Kamali, Pepperdine University*

Digital Literacy Inequality in Korea: ICT Affective Factors in Gender and Socioeconomic Gaps. *Minju Kim, Korea University; Beilei Gou, Korea University; Pey-Yan Liou, Korea University*

Identification and Measurement of "Sleeping Beauty" Patent: A Case Study of Shanghai Universities and Research Institutes. *Tianyi Sun, East China Normal University; Chunshun Yan, East China Normal University*

73.073-2. Technology, Pedagogy, and Student Learning (Table 2). SIG-Educational Change; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

AI and School Leadership in Year Two: Mapping Practitioner Messaging and Expectations. *Jayson W. Richardson, College of William & Mary; Soon-young Oh, Michigan State University*

Disturbing the Grammar of Schooling: An Ecological Analysis of Interdisciplinary Climate Change Education. *Kathryn N. Hayes, California State University - East Bay; Emily Harris, BSCS Science Learning; Eric Nolan, California State University East Bay; Karina Garbesi, California State University - East Bay*

Love What You Choose: College Students' Major Identity Under The College Entrance Examination Reform. *Ruoxi Dong, Nanjing University; Junhua Sun, Nanjing University*
To Adopt or Else? Mapping Faculty AI Integration Profiles and Systemic Barriers. *Chunling Niu, University of the Incarnate Word; Soheila Sadeghi, University of the Incarnate Word; Biao Ma, University of the Incarnate Word; Theresa Garfield Dorel, Texas A&M University - San Antonio; Melissa D. Portugal, University of the Incarnate Word;*

Brian Waltman, University of the Incarnate Word; Loren T. Cossette, University of the Incarnate Word

Affordances of Merleau-Ponty's Phenomenology: Dialogic Reading in a Chinese University. *Clara Lee Brown, The University of Tennessee - Knoxville; Rong Li, Dalian University of Technology; Joff P.N. Bradley, Teikyo University*

Chair: *Kathryn N. Hayes, California State University - East Bay*
Discussant: *Jayson W. Richardson, College of William & Mary*

73.073-3. Creative and Critical Approaches in Youth

Participatory Action Research (Table 3). SIG-Grassroots Community and Youth Organizing for Educational Justice; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Activist, Ally, Organizer, Advocate: Do the Labels Civically Engaged Youth Use for Themselves Matter? *Jerusha O. Conner, Villanova University; Emily Greytak, ACLU*

Exploring Nuances of Youth Programs That Develop Latinx Youth Wellbeing. *Carlos R. Casanova, Arizona State University; Jami Carmichael, Arizona State University; Lydia Ross, Arizona State University*

Voices of Tomorrow: Cultivating Critical Hope Through Youth Participatory Action Research. *Seth Hull*

Public Lauding, Private Wounding; Contact Zones, Structured Exclusion, and Unequally Distributed Wounds in/through Higher Education. *Ifesinachi J. Ezugwu, University of Alabama; Miguel Casar, University of Alabama; Elizabeth Delgado, UCLA; Andres R. Martinez, Los Angeles Unified School District; Chisom Okereke, UCLA; Iris Hinh, University of California - Los Angeles; Kimberly Guox, UCLA; Lucy L Flattery-Vickness, University of California - Los Angeles; Thera Boonyamarn, UCLA; Claire Li, UCLA*

Exploring the Educational Experiences of Afghan Refugee Youth in Canada: A Photovoice Study. *Narjes Hashemi, McGill University*

Chair: *Alexandra Allweiss, Michigan State University*

Discussant: *Alexandra Allweiss, Michigan State University*

73.073-4. Critique of the Critical (Table 4). SIG-Marxian

Analysis of Society, Schools and Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Critical Realism for Marxist Critical Education. *Alpesh Maisuria, University of the West of England*

Decolonial critical pedagogy based on decolonial Marxism.

Raul Olmo Fregoso Bailón, University of Nevada - Reno
(Re)reading Althusser in the 2020s: Toward a more complex sense of ideology in education. *Zachary A. Casey, Rhodes College*

Chair: *Jesus Jaime-Diaz, Colorado State University Pueblo*

73.073-5. Innovating Middle Grades Curriculum and Pedagogy: Inquiry, Literacy, and STEM Integration (Table 5). SIG-Middle-Level Education Research;

Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Advancing STEM Interest Development: A Quasi-Experimental Study of the iBEARS Intervention. *Morgan R. Castillo, Baylor University; Liesel Lutz, Baylor University; Maryann R. Hebda; Kailah Hall, Baylor University; Katherine McIntosh, Baylor University; Tracey N. Sulak, Baylor University*

Participatory Prismatic Evaluation: An Ontological Examination of Middle Grades English Language Arts Curriculum. *Kathleen M. Brinegar, University of Vermont; Cee Carter, University of Vermont*

Understanding Middle School Teachers' Content Knowledge and Pedagogical Content Knowledge of the Nature of Science. *Austin Wilson, Georgia College & State University; Rui Kang, Georgia College & State University*

World of Wonder: Young Adolescent Inquiry Through Virtual Reality and Supported Research Opportunities. *Lindsay E. Persohn, University of South Florida Sarasota-Manatee; Lucy Monette, University of South Florida; Leah Burger, University of South Florida; Cheryl R. Ellerbrock, University of South Florida*

Chair: *Amanda Wall, Georgia Southern University*

73.073-6. Discussing Liberatory Praxis and Freirean Pedagogy (Table 6). SIG-Paulo Freire; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Educators Critically Reflect on the Surveillance & Regulation of Gender Expression in Schools. *Amanda J. Cordova, North Dakota State University*

Ímpetu Del Corazón Maternal: Immigrant Latina Mothers and the Pedagogy of Acompañamiento. *Cristal B. Flores, Chapman University*

Reframing Boundaries: Teachers' Perspectives on Language Diversity in Early Childhood Classrooms. *Ana Luisa Borba Gediel, Federal University of Viçosa*

Chair: *Laura Fittz Parks, Fort Lewis College*

73.073-7. Application of meta-analytic methods to multi-site randomized controlled trials in educational interventions (Table 7). SIG-Research on Evaluation; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 9:45-11:15am

Participant:

Mixed-Method Pilot Study: Designing a Survey on Evaluation

Capacity in Institutional Research. *Giang Huynh, Claremont Graduate University*

73.073-8. How Research-Practice Partnership Collaboration Can Inform Education Policy and Practice: Examples from Los Angeles (Table 8). SIG-Research Use; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Supporting Implementation of an Ethnic Studies Policy Using Research From a Long-Term Research-Practice Partnership. *Kyo Yamashiro, Loyola Marymount University; Lucrecia Santibanez, University of California - Los Angeles; Estevan Leyva, Los Angeles Unified School District*

Using Research on Math Tracking to Inform School District Approaches to Math Course Access. *Carrie Miller, University of California - Los Angeles; Meredith Phillips, University of California - Los Angeles; Mollie Rudnick, Los Angeles Unified School District*

Chair: *Jordan Rickles, University of California - Los Angeles*

73.073-9. Placing Students At Promise with Small Instruction, Adolescent Achievement Predictors, and Warm Demander Pedagogy (Table 9). SIG-Talent Development of Students Placed at Risk; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Does Access to Small Group Instruction and Individual Tutoring Close the Achievement Gap? *Karyn Ginesi, Notre Dame of Maryland University; Mark J. Fenster, Notre Dame of Maryland University; Joanna Newton, Notre Dame of Maryland University*

Learning Difficulty and Depression Symptoms as Predictors of Academic Achievement Among Adolescents: A Cross-Lagged Study from China. *Xiaojie Cao, East China Normal University*

Warm Demander Pedagogy and Academic Competence: Academic Self-Efficacy as a Mediator. *Camille Warner, Lincoln University; Debra Roberts, Howard University*

73.073-10. Mentoring Frameworks and Campus Dynamics (Table 10). SIG-Mentorship and Mentoring Practices; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Academic mentoring and the reproduction of culture: discourses, identities, and institutional tensions in Chile. *Maria Fernanda Goñi, CIAE Universidad de Chile; Nicole Estrella González, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile; Daniela Véliz Calderón, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile*

A Humanizing Pedagogy of Justice-Oriented Mentorship. *Christine W Nganga, The George Washington University; Naudia Fairclough, The George Washington University*

Reconceptualizing Doctoral Mentoring: A Reciprocal Approach to Professional Learning for Mentor-Mentee Dyads. *Faiza M. Jamil, Clemson University; Nora D. Hochstetter, Clemson University*

Chair: *Robin Brandehoff, University of Colorado - Denver*

73.074. AERA Roundtable Session Saturday 9:45 am - Gold 4;
Roundtable Session

73.074-1. Expanding Definitions of Literacies Through Embodied Practices (Table 1). SIG-Writing and Literacies; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Collaborative Embodied Composing: Reimagining Individualized Literacy Practices through Drama. *Jacqueline Wunsch, University of Pennsylvania*

Redefining How the Game is Played: Black Male Athletes and the Politics of Officiating Literacy and Literacy Practices.

Mario Worlds, California State University - Fullerton

Turning Points Along Embodied Pathways: Attending to Children's Ephemeral Encounters with the Arts. *Luke Max Muscat, St. Luke's School*

73.074-2. (Re)defining and Exploring the Possibilities of Literacy Teaching, Learning, and Assessment in the K-12 Classroom (Table 2). SIG-Writing and Literacies; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Literacy for Self-Discovery: Critical Conversations in the Secondary ELA Classroom. *Katie F. Whitley, Montclair State University*

Teaching Argumentative Writing: Three Rhetorical Situations in a Culturally and Linguistically Diverse Secondary English Classroom. *George E. Newell, The Ohio State University; Amanda White, Columbus City Schools; Kevin Fulton, The Ohio State University; Tzu-Jung Lin, The Ohio State University*

Beyond Fragmentation: A Multidimensional Approach to Literacy Learning. *Kelly C Johnston, Baylor University*

Redefining Correctness in Writing Assessments: A Modified Delphi Study on Culturally Responsive Scoring. *Lindy Johnson, Michigan State University; Adrea Truckenmiller, Michigan State University; Lakeisha Johnson, Florida State University; Ellie Friedman, Michigan State University; Samantha Bourgeois, Michigan State University*

Chair: *Kyle P. Smith, University of Michigan*

73.074-3. AI in Assessment and Reasoning: Innovations in Measurement and Scale Development (Table 3). Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- Alignment Between Factor Names and Item Texts in Psychological Assessments. *Mingfeng Xue, University of North Carolina - Greensboro; He Ren, University of Washington; Yunting Liu, University of California - Berkeley*
- Automated Generation of Verbal Analogical Reasoning Items: An AI-augmented Cognitive Item Design Approach. *Yue Wang, East China Normal University; Xiangdong Yang, East China Normal University*
- Expectation and Its Change Over Time: A Within-Subject Study of Chatbot Expectations and Learning Experience. *Songhee Han, Florida State University; Jueun Shin, Florida State University; Jiyeon Han, Florida State University*
- Is AI Smart Enough to Identify the Right Factors? A Pilot Study on AI-Based Scale Development for Subjective Topics. *Eunji Lee, University of Georgia; George Engelhard, University of Georgia; Zhenqiu Laura Lu, University of Georgia; Yoojoong Kim, University of Georgia*
- LLM Raters of Writing and Reasoning: Towards Valid and Efficient Automated Assessment. *John Rolfe Robertson, University of Maryland; Teresa Garcia, University of Maryland; Melike Hanedar, University of Maryland; Doug Lombardi, University of Maryland*

Chair: *Zhaochen Gu, University of Illinois at Chicago*

73.074-4. New Landscapes, New Visions: Reimagining Adult Education (Table 4). SIG-Adult Literacy and Adult Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- Constructing a New Vision for Immigrant Adult Education: A Framework of Intentional Teaching Practices for Adult Educators. *Emily Dobrich, University of Toronto - OISE*
- Facebook as a Literacy Landscape: (Un)Bordering Languacultural Repertoires of Recently Resettled Bhutanese and Karen Refugee Adults in the U.S. *Xia Chao, Duquesne University*
- GSB: Reimagining Adult Literacy with Dignity and Humanity Introduction. *Ozivil Ecford, Northwestern University; Heather Lindahl, Evanston Public Library; Michael S. Horn, Northwestern University*
- Living Literature: A Narrative Inquiry into The Crowned Sisterhood Book Club. *Diana Quito, Rollins College*
- Rethinking Persistence: Noncredit Adult High School Diploma Students' Protracted Persistence Across Their Educational Trajectories. *Liliana Martinez-Kaufman, University of*

California - Los Angeles

Chair: *Alicia Rusoja, University of California - Davis*

73.074-5. Elevating Student Voices in Online Learning Environments (Table 5). SIG-Online Teaching and Learning; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- From Information to Transformation: Arts-Based Online Learning for Social Justice. *Yisha Zhao, University of Washington; Charles A. Peck, University of Washington*
- Technology-Enhanced Peer Learning Communities: Investigating Social Capital Formation in Online Doctoral Education. *Lei Wang, Auburn University - Montgomery*
- The Entanglement of Culturally Responsive Teaching with Online Learning Environments: Pedagogy, Politics, and Technology. *YangHyun Kim, City University of New York; Alex Kumi-Yeboah, University at Albany - SUNY; Woomok Jeong, University of Wisconsin - Madison*
- Webcams On, Unequal Costs for Girls: Gender Disparities in Depressive Symptoms, Academic Engagement, and Achievement tied to Universal Webcam-On Norms during Remote Learning. *Sharlyn Ferguson-Johnson, Michigan State University*

Chair: *Lina Safa, Pepperdine University*

73.074-6. Designing for Inclusion – Universal Design, Digital Access, and Validity (Table 6). SIG-Inclusion and Accessibility in Educational Assessment; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- Assessment Validity in Peril: An Analysis of State Policies on Testing Personnel Qualifications. *Mari Quanbeck, National Center on Educational Outcomes; Virginia A. Ressa, University of Minnesota; Andrew R. Hinkle, National Center on Educational Outcomes; Sheryl S. Lazarus, University of Minnesota*
- Integrating Culturally Responsive Assessments with Instruction for L2 Learners: A Systematic Review. *Semi J. Yeom, Defense Language Institute; Young Ae Kim, Defense Language Institute*
- Universally Designed Digital Textbooks for Equitable Learning: A Comparative European Study. *Vanessa Macchia, Free University - Bozen-Bolzano; Stefania Torri, Free University - Bozen-Bolzano; Maxim Brnic, University of Münster; Sven Degenhardt, University of Hamburg; Sarah Edelsbrunner, Technical University of Graz; Tom Erdel, Centre pour le développement des compétences relatives à la vue; Gilbert Greefrath, University of Münster; Bernhard Kargl, Technical University of Graz; Hannah Lathan, University of Vechta; Leif Mönter, University of Vechta;*

Sandra Schön, Technical University of Graz; Marie-Luise Schütt, University of Hamburg; Mike Wetzel, Centre pour le développement des compétences relatives à la vue
Validating Basic Psychological Need Satisfaction Scale for Students with Disability Accommodation in Hyflex. *Elnara Mammadova, Purdue University; Nathan Mentzer, Purdue University*

Chair: *Lindsay Ruhter, University of Kansas*

73.074-7. Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses of Reading, Writing, and Literacy Instruction (Table 7). SIG-Research in Reading and Literacy; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

A Systematic Review of Culturally Relevant Reading Instruction for Students with Disabilities and Reading Difficulties. *Alexandra Shelton, Johns Hopkins University; Jerae Kelly, University of Hawai'i at Manoa; Irene Ramirez, Johns Hopkins University; Yang Fu, University of Maryland*

Cursive Handwriting Instructional Practices and Assessments: A Systematic Review. *Murphy Young, University of Iowa; Shawn Datchuk, University of Iowa*

Effects of Reading Comprehension Interventions on the Reading Outcomes of Middle School Students with Dyslexia. *Oluwabunmi Blessing Alao, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

The Relations of Morphological Awareness and Syntactic Awareness with L2 English Reading Comprehension: A Meta-Analysis. *Yanfang Zeng, Texas A&M University; Li-Jen Kuo, Texas A&M University; Xiaojie Zhang, Texas A&M University*

A Meta-Analysis of Computer-Assisted Word Reading Interventions for Elementary School Students: Effects on Accuracy, Fluency, and Comprehension. *Ali Jahanaray, Clemson University; Alireza Kassirian, University of Nevada, Las Vegas; Mohammad Jahanaray, Virginia Commonwealth University*

Chair: *Qingli Lei, University of Illinois Chicago*

73.074-8. Giftedness, Creativity, and Talent Roundtable: Conceptual Understandings in Creativity (Table 8). SIG-Research on Giftedness, Creativity and Talent; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Generative AI and Creativity in K–12 Education: A Systematic Scoping Review of the Literature from 2017 to 2025. *Seyedahmad Rahimi, University of Florida; Salah Esmailigoujar, University of Florida; Maryam Babae, University of Florida; Christopher J. Dede, Harvard University*

Conceptual Connections of Giftedness and Creativity: A

Systematic Review of Gifted Education Journals (2005–2024). *Jeb S Puryear, University of Montana; Kristen N. Lamb, University of Alabama; Melanie S. Meyer, Baylor University; Lindsay Ellis Lee, Advanced Learning Research & Consulting, LLC*

Can Generative AI influence creativity? A Meta-Analysis. *Shuyu Wang, University of Connecticut; Yuyue Wang, Syracuse University*

Chair: *Jeb Puryear, University of Montana - Missoula*

73.074-9. Generative AI, Identity, and Cognitive Partnership (Table 9). SIG-Technology, Instruction, Cognition & Learning; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Are Teachers Addicted to AI? Analyzing Factors on Generative AI Through the I-PACE Model. *Mi Tang, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Yiran Du, University of Cambridge*

Building AI Learner Identity Across Career Aspirations: An Expectancy-Value Perspective. *Fan Xu, N/A; Shiyun Jiang, North Carolina State University; Suzhen Duan, Towson University; Liu Dong, Purdue University; Chi-Jia Hsieh, Purdue University; Dan Sun, Hangzhou Normal University*

ChatGPT as Cognitive Partner: A Mixed-Methods Study with Puerto Rican University Students. *Samuel Colón De La Rosa, University of Puerto Rico - Río Piedras*

CROSS Cultures: Exploring the Roles of Generative AI in Enhancing Multicultural Education. *Keyi Zhou, University of Hong Kong; Jing Luo, The university of Minnesota; Chin-Hsi Lin, University of Hong Kong*

Figuring GenAI: Toward a Technocurious Framework in History Education. *Amy E. Allen, Virginia Tech; David Hicks, Virginia Tech*

Chair: *Chaewon Kim, Florida State University*

73.074-10. Innovating for Impact in K-12 Schools: Leveraging Technology to Enhance Engagement, Ethics, and Instructional Effectiveness (Table 10). Division H - Research, Evaluation and Assessment in Schools; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Mapping Educational Technology Engagement Trajectories and Math Growth in Elementary Schools. *Huan Liu, IXL Learning; Mary Hargis, IXL Learning; Xiaozhu An, IXL Learning; Bozhidar M. Bashkov, IXL Learning*

Promoting Middle School Students' Ethical Awareness of AI: Findings From a Cluster Randomized Trial. *Tianyang Xu, Michigan State University; Xuesen Cheng, Michigan State University*

Towards the Improvement of Teaching Practices: Educational

Design Research Supporting “1:1 technology” Programs.
Carolanne Boulanger, Laval University; Geraldine
Heilporn, University of Sherbrooke

Chair: Tingting Li, Washington State University

Division and SIG Posters

73.075. AERA Poster Session Saturday 9:45 am; Poster Session

73.075-1. AI and Technology Integration in K-12 Education.

Division C - Learning and Instruction; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall -
Exhibit Hall A; 9:45-11:15am

Posters:

1. AI vs. Parent: Supporting Early Literacy at Home Through Conversational Agents (Poster 1). *Shuang Quan, Juniata College; Laney E. Gerdich, Juniata College; Tatum E. Livelsberger, Juniata College; Xintian Tu-Shea, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Qingxiao Zheng, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Yao Du, University of Southern California; Yi Ding, Fordham University*
2. An Empirical Framework for Assessing AI in Early Childhood Education: A Global vs. Local Perspective (Poster 2). *Sihang Yu, The Education University of Hong Kong; Yichen Hou, The Education University of Hong Kong; Hui Li, The Education University of Hong Kong*
3. A Systematic Review of AI Integration in STEM Education: Motivation, Engagement, Efficiency, and Adaptivity (Poster 3). *Chenxi Zhou, The George Washington University*
4. Bridging Reading Science and EdTech: A Framework for Evaluating Early Literacy Tools (Poster 4). *Angelica DaSilva, Joan Ganz Cooney Center at Sesame Workshop; Diane Baty Gifford, Southern Methodist University; Medha Tare, Sesame Workshop*
5. Cognitive Networks in AI Collaboration Pre-service Math Teachers' Problem-Solving Patterns (Poster 5). *Shuai Zhang, East China Normal University; Binyan Xu, East China Normal University*
6. Comparing Children's Verbal Engagement with an Interactive Media Character and a Human during Video Watching (Poster 6). *Nikki Nasser, University of California - Irvine; Kunlei He, University of California - Irvine; Mark Warschauer, University of California - Irvine*
7. Designing for Procedural Flexibility with Collaborative Digital Whiteboards: A Case Study of Middle School Algebra (Poster 7). *Seiyon Lee, University of Florida; Shan Zhang, University of Florida; Hongming Li, University of Florida; Anthony Botelho, University of Florida*
8. Early Childhood Teachers' Perceptions and Use of Digital Technology in the United Arab Emirates (Poster 8). *Charles Raffaele, New York University; Basel Hussein, New York University; Hala Sukkar, New York University; Khadija Alhashmi, New York University; Antje von Suchodoletz, New York University - Abu Dhabi; Bruce D. Homer, Graduate Center - CUNY; Jan L. Plass, New York University*
9. Examining Children's Scientific Misconceptions from an Educational Video with an Embedded Conversational Agent (Poster 9). *Nikki Nasser, University of California - Irvine; Kunlei He, University of California - Irvine; Mark Warschauer, University of California - Irvine*
10. Exploring AI Integration in K-12 Classrooms: A Case Study of Teachers' Experiences with Khanmigo (Poster 10). *Kolawole Michael Afolabi, Oklahoma State University; Katherine A. Curry, Oklahoma State University; Oguns Clement Audu, Oklahoma State University; Marcia Sun, Oklahoma State University; Dominic Siami Egure, Oklahoma State University*
11. Exploring Critical Engagement with GAI in Academic Writing: A Mixed-Methods Study (Poster 11). *Qi Sun, University at Albany - SUNY; Shengkai Yin, Federation University Australia*
12. Fostering Higher-Order Thinking with Generative AI: A Meta-Analysis (Poster 12). *Mingchen Wei, East China Normal University; Hao Lei, East China Normal University; Longyue Fang, East China Normal University*
13. How Does AI Impact Student Learning? An Umbrella Review of Promises, Pitfalls, and Research Gaps (Poster 13). *Qiyang Lin, Michigan State University; Fangzheng Zhao, Nanjing Normal University; Yuli Shao, New York University; Amédee Marchand Martella, University of Georgia*
14. Impact of GenAI Usage on Primary School Students' Learning Outcomes in ICT Course (Poster 14). *Jie Xu, Zhejiang University; Yan Li, Zhejiang University*
15. Learning STEM with Generative AI: A Pilot Case Study of Black Elementary Students' Experiences (Poster 15). *Anike Sakariyawo, Florida International University*

73.075-2. Amplifying Participants' Perspectives to Enhance Learning Environments.

Division C - Learning and Instruction; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall -
Exhibit Hall A; 9:45-11:15am

Posters:

16. Challenges and Evidence that Matter for Solutions: Implications for Invention Education Programs (Poster 16). *Tamara Galoyan, Massachusetts Institute of Technology; Audra Skukauskaite, University of Central Florida; Stephanie Couch, Massachusetts Institute of Technology*
17. Developing Sustainability-oriented Marine Scientists: Integrating Socio-scientific Issues in Authentic Ocean Contexts in Higher Education (Poster 17). *Wei-Ting Li, National Sun Yat-sen University; Shuo-Chian Joe Shiu, National Sun Yat-sen University; Paichi Shein, National Sun Yat-sen University*
18. Differential Association of Teacher Support on Academic and Psychological Adjustment: Evidence from a Meta-Analysis (Poster 18). *Yeonggyeong Cha, Korea National*

University of Education; Moonbee Kang, Korea National University of Education; Hanyeong Kim, Korea National University of Education; Yeonsu Shin, Korea National University of Education; Yuseon Choi, Korea National University of Education; Juyeon Song, Korea National University of Education

19. Humanizing AI Grading: Student-Centered Insights on Fairness, Trust, Consistency and Transparency (Poster 19). *Bahare Riahi, North Carolina State University; Viktoriia Storozhevykh, North Carolina State University; Veronica Catete, North Carolina State University*
20. "It's just another teaching tool": Perspectives of university instructors on integrating maker pedagogy (Poster 20). *Yumiko Murai, Simon Fraser University; Zi Lin, Simon Fraser University; Mitra Nikimaleki, Simon Fraser University*
21. Playing and Learning Together in a Multiplayer Data Science Education Game World (Poster 21). *Tianyu Ma, University of Miami; Jennifer Beth Kahn, University of Miami*
22. Supporting Responsive Teaching with GenAI-Powered Formative Assessment (Poster 22). *Idris Solola, Utah State University; Ravi Sinha, Utah State University; Hillary Lucille Swanson, Utah State University; Rida Munir, Utah State University; Ha Nguyen, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*

73.075-3. Learning Together: Collaboration, Teaching Strategies, and Identity in Classroom and Community Contexts. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Poster Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 9:45-11:15am

Posters:

23. From Cooperation to Collaboration: How Assessment Drives Collaborative Shift (Poster 23). *Tsung-Liang Tsai, Taipei Medical University, Taiwan*
24. Coding Music Together: How Elementary Computer Science Students Collaboratively Translate Musical Ideas into Code (Poster 24). *Chelsi R Miller, Northwestern University; Cameron Luke Roberts, Northwestern University; Michael S. Horn, Northwestern University*
25. Investigating the temporality of group engagement dynamics toward intellectual progress (Poster 25). *Toni Kempler Rogat, Purdue University; Anne Traynor, Purdue University; Cindy E. Hmelo-Silver, Indiana University; Britte Haugan Cheng, Menlo Education Research; Temitope F. Adeoye Olenloa, Purdue University; Alexandria Holmes, Purdue University*
26. Toward a Multimodal Micro-Ecological Methodology for Analyzing Active Listening in Collaborative Problem Solving (Poster 26). *Xiaomeng Huang, New York University; Xavier Ochoa, New York University*
27. Dialogic Preschool Classroom Talk and Variabilities by

Instructional Content: An Explanatory Sequential Mixed Methods Study (Poster 27). *Monica Lu, The Ohio State University*

28. Unraveling the Relationship between Dialogic Teaching Strategies and Students' Creative Thinking: A Multimethod Approach (Poster 28). *Yang Tao, Nanjing University; Gaowei Chen, University of Hong Kong*
29. Classroom Relationship Profiles: Links with Students' Multiple Goals and Self-Regulated Learning Strategy Use (Poster 29). *Qingyao Dan, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Barry Bai, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Yuhong Jiao, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Hongfang Li, Baicaooyuan Kindergarten; Jiatong Zhang, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; To Chan, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Miranda Lin, Illinois State University*
30. When Digital Becomes Personal: Emotions Mediate Teachers' Support and Primary Students' Self-Regulation in English E-Learning (Poster 30). *Yu Su, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Barry Bai, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Yuhong Jiao, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Jiatong Zhang, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Qingyao Dan, The Chinese University of Hong Kong*
31. The Role of Teachers' Strategic Mindset in Effective Teaching Practices (Poster 31). *Seulki Chin, University of Texas at Austin; Katherine M. Muenks, University of Texas at Austin; Patricia Chen, University of Texas at Austin*
32. Self-Belief Against the Grain: How Youth Mobilize Constraint to Form Self-Perception (Poster 32). *Xinxin Feng, University of Washington; Jason Yip, University of Washington - Seattle; Yacqub Ahmed, University of Washington*
33. Integrating Culture and Science Inquiry Learning for Taiwan's Urban Indigenous Youth (Poster 33). *Shu-Huei Yen, Rong-Shan AI Education Application and Promotion Association; Hui-Min Chou, Academia Sinica*
34. Early Care and Education Professionals Talk About Race (Poster 34). *Gisele Crawford, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Allison De Marco, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Clare Wongwai, University of Illinois at Chicago; Iheoma U. Iruka, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Sandra L. Soliday Hong, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Laura Kuhn, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Zachary Price, Towson University; Kalen Donahue, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*
35. The Personal and Emotional Costs of Black Male Teacher Empathy: A Case Study (Poster 35). *Joseph Eisman, Purdue University; Kendra Yvonne Hall, Old Dominion University*
36. The Lab: A Collaborative Autoethnography on Building a Peer Support System for Black Women Scholars (Poster 36). *Taylor Cummings, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; British Reynolds, University of Illinois at Chicago; Stacy Seward, University of Massachusetts - Lowell; Doretha Lewis, Capella University; Kendra Seraphine, Wake Forest University*

73.075-4. Counseling Poster Session B. Division E - Counseling and Human Development; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 9:45-11:15am

Posters:

37. Echoes from the Hallway: Counselor Voices on Bullying, Barriers, and Breakthroughs (Poster 37). *Servet Altan, MEF University; Hande Özkan, MEF University; Ezgi Toplu-Demirtas, MEF University*
38. Factors Associated with Retention in a Randomized Couple Education Program (Poster 38). *Tiejun Zhang, University of South Carolina; Ryan G. Carlson, University of South Carolina; Ruiqin Gao, University of South Carolina; Violet Hodge, University of South Carolina*
39. How counselors in different school locales allocate their time across a range of service areas (Poster 39). *Kelvin Tosin Afolabi, University of Texas at Arlington; Thuy Dang, University of Texas at Arlington*
40. "Listening beyond words": Unforgetting histories in bilingual counseling (Poster 40). *Mariana L. Sánchez, University of Maryland; Marina Sanchez, The George Washington University*
41. Motivations for Social Media Use and Body Dissatisfaction among Latinx Undergraduate Students (Poster 41). *Alex Soto, University of Houston-Downtown; Alejandra Alvarado, University of Houston-Downtown; Danya Marie Serrano, Allan Hancock College*
42. Navigating Borders and Bytes: The Reconstruction of Parenting Narratives by Chinese Immigrant Mothers (Poster 42). *Xu Zhao, University of Calgary; Dongzhao Liu, University of Calgary*
43. Padres Ayudando Padres: A Community-Based Parenting Support Group Built by and for Immigrant Mothers (Poster 43). *Maribel Tohara Nakamatsu, George Mason University; Rachael Goodman, George Mason University*
44. Promoting Reflection and Connection: A School Counselor-Led Mindfulness-Based Consultation Intervention with Middle School Teachers (Poster 44). *Citlali Molina, Texas Christian University; Nancy Chae, University of San Diego; Hyunhee Kim, Johns Hopkins University; Dominique Hill, University of Georgia; Matthew Lemberger-Truelove, University of North Texas*
45. Resilience Among Adolescents in Out-of-Home Residential Care and Community Schools: Individual, Family and School Contributions (Poster 45). *Michal Hanouka, Tel Aviv University; Michal Al-Yagon, Tel Aviv University*
46. School Counselors as Change Agents: Transforming Support Systems for Multilingual Learners (Poster 46). *Soomin Chao, California State University - Fullerton; Gabrielle Aquino-Adriatico, California State University - Fullerton*
47. School Development Consultancy: Assessing the Quality, Benefits, and Effectiveness (Poster 47). *Stephan Gerhard*

Huber, Johannes Kepler University of Linz; Andrea Thaller, Johannes Kepler University of Linz

48. Schools as Sites of Mandated Reporting: Insights from a National Survey of School Social Workers (Poster 48). *Erin Sugrue, Augsburg University; Ashley-Marie H. Daftary, University of Nevada - Reno*
49. Stages of Psychological Help-seeking among Parents of Primary and Secondary School Students: A Qualitative Research (Poster 49). *Jiayi Yang, Beijing Normal University; Linyuan Deng, Beijing Normal University; Yuchen Yang, Beijing No.4 High School; Qingjiu Cao, Peking University Sixth Hospital*

73.075-5. Teaching in the Key of Liberation: From Jim Crow to AI Literacies. SIG-Research Focus on Black Education; Poster Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 9:45-11:15am

Posters:

50. Writing Futures from the Margin: AI, Black Literacies, and Speculative Counter-Narratives at an HBCU (Poster 50). *Shahin Hossain, University of Maryland - Baltimore County; Ariadne Jevnikar, Lakehead University*
51. Affirming the Phonological Genius of Black Language: Linguistic Justice in Foundational Literacy (Poster 51). *Jasmyn K. Jones, University of Memphis*
52. To Educators, With Love: Leveraging Black Children's Emergent Sociopolitical Understandings as Resources in Teacher Learning (Poster 52). *Natalie R. Davis, University of Michigan*

Chair: *Sosanya M. Jones, Howard University*

73.075-6. Graduate and Postdoctoral Education across the Disciplines Poster Session. SIG-Graduate and Postdoctoral Education across the Disciplines; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 9:45-11:15am

Poster:

53. A Conversation on the Emerging Phenomenon of Post-Doctoral Graduation Blues (Poster 53). *Amanda J. Rockinson-Szapkiw, University of Memphis; Lucinda S. Spaulding, University of Lynchburg; Elizabeth DeBolt, Liberty University*

73.076. e-Lightning Ed-Talk Session 16 - Stage 1. AERA e-Lightning Ed-Talks; AERA Ed Talk
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Exhibit Hall A - Stage 1; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

The Lab: A Collaborative Autoethnography on Building a Peer Support System for Black Women Scholars (Stage 1, 9:50 AM). *Taylor Cummings, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; British Reynolds, University of Illinois at Chicago; Stacy Seward, University of Massachusetts - Lowell; Doretha*

Lewis, Capella University; Kendra Seraphine, Wake Forest University

Early Care and Education Professionals Talk About Race (Stage 1, 9:59 AM). *Gisele Crawford, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Allison De Marco, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Clare Wongwai, University of Illinois at Chicago; Iheoma U. Iruka, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Sandra L. Soliday Hong, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Laura Kuhn, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*

Self-Belief Against the Grain: How Youth Mobilize Constraint to Form Self-Perception (Stage 1, 10:08 AM). *Xinxin Feng, University of Washington; Jason Yip, University of Washington - Seattle; Yacqub Ahmed, University of Washington*

The Role of Teachers' Strategic Mindset in Effective Teaching Practices (Stage 1, 10:17 AM). *Seulki Chin, University of Texas at Austin; Katherine M. Muenks, University of Texas at Austin; Patricia Chen, University of Texas at Austin*

Toward a Multimodal Micro-Ecological Methodology for Analyzing Active Listening in Collaborative Problem Solving (Stage 1, 10:26 AM). *Xiaomeng Huang, New York University; Xavier Ochoa, New York University*

Stages of Psychological Help-seeking among Parents of Primary and Secondary School Students: A Qualitative Research (Stage 1, 10:35 AM). *Jiayi Yang, Beijing Normal University; Linyuan Deng, Beijing Normal University; Yuchen Yang, Beijing No.4 High School; Qingjiu Cao, Peking University Sixth Hospital*

Resilience Among Adolescents in Out-of-Home Residential Care and Community Schools: Individual, Family and School Contributions (Stage 1, 10:44 AM). *Michal Hanouka, Tel Aviv University; Michal Al-Yagon, Tel Aviv University*

Padres Ayudando Padres: A Community-Based Parenting Support Group Built by and for Immigrant Mothers (Stage 1, 10:53 AM). *Maribel Tohara Nakamatsu, George Mason University; Rachael Goodman, George Mason University*

Writing Futures from the Margin: AI, Black Literacies, and Speculative Counter-Narratives at an HBCU (Stage 1, 11:02 AM). *Shahin Hossain, University of Maryland - Baltimore County; Ariadne Jevnikar, Lakehead University*

Chair: *Linda Reddy, Rutgers University*

73.077. e-Lightning Ed-Talk Session 16 - Stage 2. AERA e-Lightning Ed-Talks; AERA Ed Talk
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Exhibit Hall A - Stage 2; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Supporting Responsive Teaching with GenAI-Powered Formative Assessment (Stage 2, 9:50 AM). *Idris Solola, Utah State University; Ravi Sinha, Utah State University; Hillary Lucille Swanson, Utah State University; Rida Munir, Utah State University; Ha Nguyen, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*

Developing Sustainability-oriented Marine Scientists: Integrating Socio-scientific Issues in Authentic Ocean Contexts in Higher Education (Stage 2, 9:59 AM). *Wei-Ting Li, National Sun Yat-sen University; Shuo-Chian Joe Shiu, National Sun Yat-sen University; Paichi Shein, National Sun Yat-sen University*

Humanizing AI Grading: Student-Centered Insights on Fairness, Trust, Consistency and Transparency (Stage 2, 10:08 AM). *Bahare Riahi, North Carolina State University; Viktoriia Storozhevykh, North Carolina State University; Veronica Catete, North Carolina State University*

"It's just another teaching tool": Perspectives of university instructors on integrating maker pedagogy (Stage 2, 10:17 AM). *Yumiko Murai, Simon Fraser University; Zi Lin, Simon Fraser University; Mitra Nikimaleki, Simon Fraser University*

Playing and Learning Together in a Multiplayer Data Science Education Game World (Stage 2, 10:26 AM). *Tianyu Ma, University of Miami; Jennifer Beth Kahn, University of Miami*

AI vs. Parent: Supporting Early Literacy at Home Through Conversational Agents (Stage 2, 10:35 AM). *Shuang Quan, Juniata College; Laney E. Gerdich, Juniata College; Tatum E. Livelsberger, Juniata College; Xintian Tu-Shea, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Qingxiao Zheng, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Yao Du, University of Southern California; Yi Ding, Fordham University*

An Empirical Framework for Assessing AI in Early Childhood Education: A Global vs. Local Perspective (Stage 2, 10:44 AM). *Sihang Yu, The Education University of Hong Kong; Yichen Hou, The Education University of Hong Kong; Hui Li, The Education University of Hong Kong*

A Systematic Review of AI Integration in STEM Education: Motivation, Engagement, Efficiency, and Adaptivity (Stage 2, 10:53 AM). *Chenxi Zhou, The George Washington University*

Bridging Reading Science and EdTech: A Framework for Evaluating Early Literacy Tools (Stage 2, 11:02 AM). *Angelica DaSilva, Joan Ganz Cooney Center at Sesame Workshop; Diane Baty Gifford, Southern Methodist University; Medha Tare, Sesame Workshop*

Chair: *Hunter Gehlbach, Johns Hopkins University*

73.078. e-Lightning Ed-Talk Session 16 - Stage 3. AERA e-Lightning Ed-Talks; AERA Ed Talk
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Exhibit Hall A - Stage 3; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Cognitive Networks in AI Collaboration Pre-service Math Teachers' Problem-Solving Patterns (Stage 3, 9:50 AM). *Shuai Zhang, East China Normal University; Binyan Xu, East China Normal University*

Comparing Children's Verbal Engagement with an Interactive Media Character and a Human during Video Watching

(Stage 3, 9:59 AM). *Nikki Nasser, University of California - Irvine; Kunlei He, University of California - Irvine; Mark Warschauer, University of California - Irvine*

Designing for Procedural Flexibility with Collaborative Digital Whiteboards: A Case Study of Middle School Algebra (Stage 3, 10:08 AM). *Seiyon Lee, University of Florida; Shan Zhang, University of Florida; Hongming Li, University of Florida; Anthony Botelho, University of Florida*

Early Childhood Teachers' Perceptions and Use of Digital Technology in the United Arab Emirates (Stage 3, 10:17 AM). *Charles Raffaele, New York University; Basel Hussein, New York University; Hala Sukkar, New York University; Khadija Alhashmi, New York University; Antje von Suchodoletz, New York University - Abu Dhabi; Bruce D. Homer, Graduate Center - CUNY; Jan L. Plass, New York University*

Examining Children's Scientific Misconceptions from an Educational Video with an Embedded Conversational Agent (Stage 3, 10:26 AM). *Nikki Nasser, University of California - Irvine; Kunlei He, University of California - Irvine; Mark Warschauer, University of California - Irvine*

Exploring AI Integration in K-12 Classrooms: A Case Study of Teachers' Experiences with Khanmigo (Stage 3, 10:35 AM). *Kolawole Michael Afolabi, Oklahoma State University; Katherine A. Curry, Oklahoma State University; Oguns Clement Audu, Oklahoma State University; Marcia Sun, Oklahoma State University; Dominic Siami Egere, Oklahoma State University*

Exploring Critical Engagement with GAI in Academic Writing: A Mixed-Methods Study (Stage 3, 10:44 AM). *Qi Sun, University at Albany - SUNY; Shengkai Yin, Federation University Australia*

Chair: *Joseph S. Krajcik, Michigan State University*

Saturday, April 11th, 10:00 am

Division Sessions

74.010. Division I Health Professions Education Community Meeting (Closed Meeting). Division I - Education in the Professions; Board Meeting
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 408A;
10:00-11:00am

Chairs: *Toni Ungaretti, Johns Hopkins University; Peggy Gesing, Old Dominion University*

Participants: *Violet Kulo, University of Maryland - Baltimore; Yuane Jia, Rutgers University*

74.011. National Academy of Education Board Meeting.
Affiliated Groups; Board Meeting
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 6th Floor, Palace;
10:00am to 12:00pm

Saturday, April 11th, 11:45 am

Governance Meetings and Events

75.001. AERA International Relations Committee Closed Meeting. AERA Governance; Governance Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 513;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Chair: *Jaekyung Lee, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

75.002. Journal Publications Committee With Editors Closed Meeting. AERA Governance; Governance Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 518;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Chair: *John Neikirk, American Educational Research Association*

AERA Related Activities

75.010. The Art of the Possible: Remembering Lee Shulman.
AERA Related Activities; Invited Speaker Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum
C; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Chairs: *Pamela L. Grossman, University of Pennsylvania; Sam Wineburg, Stanford University*

Presidential Sessions

75.011. Advancing Justice through Transformation: Reflections on Institutional Leadership for Educational Futures. AERA Presidential Session; Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 406AB;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Chair: *Terry K. Flennaugh, Michigan State University*

Participants: *Terry K. Flennaugh, Michigan State University; Marcelle M. Haddix, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Marcos Pizarro, California State University - Los Angeles; Mariana Souto-Manning, Erikson Institute; Shabnam Koirala-Azad, University of San Francisco; Pedro A. Noguera, University of Southern California*

75.012. Ethnic Studies Futures: Unforgetting as a Path to Reimagining Education. AERA Presidential Session; Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 404AB;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Pushing for Complexity, Truth, and Freedom: A Brief History of Ethnic Studies in US Schools. *Michelle A. Purdy, Washington University in St. Louis*

“The Long-Term Civic and Educational Consequences of Ethnic Studies.”. *Sade Bonilla, University of Pennsylvania*
"We're Actually Making History": A Call to Support Teachers and Students in High School Black Studies. *Taylor Milan Hall, Learn4life Metro Atlanta Regional Education Partnership; Farzana Tabitha Saleem Adjah, Stanford University; Jessica Lee Stovall, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Voices from the Field: Ethnic Studies in Action. *Roxana Daylen Dueñas, Los Angeles Unified School District; Abram Jackson, Fine Arts Museum of San Francisco and the Black Teacher Project; Spencer Pritchard, Berkeley High School and the Black Teacher Project; Jesse Hagopian, Seattle Public Schools*

Chair: *Jessica Lee Stovall, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Discussant: *Allyson Tintiangco-Cubales, San Francisco State University*

75.013. Scaling Equity-oriented Innovations for Just Education Futures: Navigating Power Relations During Contentious Times. AERA Presidential Session; Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 409AB; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Chair: *Jennifer Higgs, University of California - Davis*

Discussant: *Cynthia E. Coburn, Northwestern University*

Panelists: *Kris D. Gutiérrez, University of California - Berkeley; Laura E. Hernandez, Learning Policy Institute; Nichole D. Pinkard, Northwestern University; Jose Eos Trinidad, University of California - Berkeley; Shirin Vossoughi, Northwestern University*

AERA Sessions

75.014. 2026 Wallace Foundation Distinguished Lecture: (Re)memory, Community-based Education, and ‘Youth Work’ as the Process of Futuring. AERA Sessions; Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 408B; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Chair: *Maisha T. Winn, Stanford University*

Presenter: *Bianca Jontae Baldrige, Harvard University*

Committee Sessions

75.015. Division L Fireside Chat: The Politics of Protection: Rethinking School Safety and Justice through Equity-

Driven Research and Policy. Graduate Student Council Cosponsored with Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Invited Speaker Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 402A; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Chairs: *Lesley Rivas, University of Texas at Austin; Michaela Perneti, University of Texas at Austin; John Diaz, University of California - San Diego*

Panelists: *John S. Rogers, University of California - Los Angeles; Julieta Rico, University of California - Los Angeles; Pedro Salcido, Los Angeles Unified School District*

75.016. From Policy Impact to Collective Action: Strengthening Minority-Serving Institutions in a Shifting Landscape. Social Justice Action Committee; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 502A; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Chair: *Leslie D. Gonzales, University of Arizona*

Discussants: *Marialexia Zaragoza, University of Pittsburgh; Marla Franco, University of Arizona; Kristine Jan Cruz Espinoza, California Lutheran University; Felisha Herrera, San Diego State University; Desiree Zuniga, Pasadena City College; Stacey Raina Speller, Howard University; Natalie Rose Youngbull, University of Oklahoma*

Division Sessions

75.017. Caring Leadership Amidst the Chaos: Elevating Care as Resistance, Intervention, and Imperative. Division A - Administration; Symposium
Westin Bonaventure, Level 2, Echo Park; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Leadership for Caring: Conditions for Teacher Learning and Development in Difficult Context. *Andrea Carrasco Saez, Universidad de Chile*

Caring Under Constraint: Guidance for School Leaders on School Structures and Ethical Practice. *Janel Anderson, Gonzaga University*

Caring for Principals’ Mental Health: A Mixed-Method Study on the Differential Impacts of Systemic Stressors. *Eleanor Su-Keene, Texas A&M University; Catie Samson, Texas A&M University; Shaun D Hutchins, Austin Independent School District*

Caring State Leadership: Exploring How State Policy Shapes Conditions for Care at the Local Level. *Kate Kennedy, University of Cincinnati; Lara Altman, Northwestern University; Jeff Walls, University of Iowa*

Queer and Trans Educational Care: An Adaptable Framework Towards Democratizing and Decolonizing Education Systems. *Andrew Stein, Northwestern University; Benjamin C. Kennedy, University of California - San Diego; William French, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Mollie*

McQuillan, University of Wisconsin - Madison

Chair: *Kate Kennedy, University of Cincinnati*

Discussant: *Rosa L. Rivera-McCutchen, Hunter College - CUNY*

75.018. Racializing and Spatializing Resistance: Contextual Equity Leadership and Policy. Division A -

Administration; Paper Session

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Palos Verdes; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

If You Want To Go Far, Go Together: Examining the Role of Community School Leadership and Black Family Collaboration in Effectively Supporting Black Students in South Central Los Angeles. *Keara L. Williams, University of California - Los Angeles*

Navigating District-Community Relationships to Achieve Equity: A Critical Policy Discourse Analysis. *Amaarah N. DeCuir, American University*

The Relationship Between Black Education and Black Family-School-Community Engagement in America: A BlackCrit Perspective. *Marissa Moore, Saint Louis University*

Towards Equity: The Relationship Between Opportunity Gaps and High School Graduation for Maryland Black Students. *Frim Ampaw, Morgan State University; Sarah Williams, Grand Valley State University; Robert Jerome Anderson, Morgan State University; Jenai Johnson, Morgan State University*

White Principals and Logics of Family and Community Engagement: Performative “Nights” to Growing Equitable Collaborations. *Lindsey J. Kaiser, University of Maine*

Discussant: *Ishmael Miller, Arizona State University*

75.019. Transformational Leadership Growth and Critical Consciousness: Learning Across Sectors, Systems, and States. Division A - Administration; Paper Session

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Los Cerritos; 11:45am to

1:15pm

Participants:

A Multi-Study Examination of Educational Leader Professional Development Experiences for Transformational Learning. *Bryan A. VanGronigen, University of Delaware; Meredith Wronowski, University of Dayton; Wesley Henry, Sacred Heart University; Katie Reynolds, University of Dayton; Adam Swinney, East Haven Public Schools*

Cross-Sector Learning for School Leaders: Enhancing Leadership Development Through Industry Collaboration. *Chun Sing Maxwell Ho, The Education University of Hong Kong; Junjun Chen, Education University of Hong Kong*

School Site Leaders who work with Principals’ Professional Learning: Needs, Opportunities & Insights. *Rebecca Cheung, University of California - Berkeley; Melissa Itzel Virrueta-Peters, University of California - Berkeley; Jessica G. Rigby, University of Washington; Annie Wilhelm, Southern Methodist University*

The criticality of consciousness in leadership preparation and professional development. *Shannon Renee Waite, Howard University*

Chair: *Maria L Lawson-Davenport, Norfolk State University*

Discussant: *LeAnne C. Salazar Montoya, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*

75.020. Bridging Equity Gaps in STEM: Insights from the Upcoming Handbook on Gender and STEM. Division C -

Learning and Instruction Cosponsored with SIG-Motivation in Education; Symposium

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Beaudry B; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Addressing Gendered Math Confidence During Primary School Years: Intervention Efforts Targeting Beliefs about Math Ability. *Hyun Ji Lee, Hunter College, The City University of New York; Mimi Bong, Korea University*

Links Between Gender Stereotypes and Gender Gaps in STEM Motivation in Childhood and Adolescence. *Paul Anthony Turcotte, University of Houston; Sydney Baker, University of Houston; Kahyun Lee, University of Houston; Allison Master, University of Houston*

Charting the Nuances in the Group Differences and Changes in Youths’ Motivational Beliefs: Insights from Multiple Datasets. *Sandra D. Simpkins, University of California - Irvine; Charlott Rubach, University of Rostock; Glona Lee-Poon, University of California - Irvine; Hyewon Lee, University of California - Irvine; Miranda G. Goldstein, University of California - Irvine; Jacquelynne S. Eccles, University of California - Irvine*

The Motivational Benefits of Observing and Serving as a Role Model for Minoritized College Students. *Kevin Francisco Ramirez, University of California - Berkeley; Hye Rin Lee, University of Georgia; Xiao-Yin Chen, University of Tennessee*

Doctor or Engineer: Gendered Motivational Processes that Shape Within-STEM Educational and Career Choices. *Yichi Zhang, University of Georgia; Harlee Robinson DiNello, University of Georgia; Emily Quinn Rosenzweig, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Chairs: *Xiao-Yin Chen, University of Tennessee; Hye Rin Lee, University of Georgia*

Discussant: *Kristy A. Robinson, McGill University*

75.021. Critical Narratives From Carceral, Educational, and Community Contexts. Division C - Learning and

Instruction Cosponsored with SIG-Family, School, Community Partnerships; Paper Session

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, La Brea; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

An Enactivist Grounded Theory on Constructing a Democratic School Community. *Halil Han Aktas, Erzincan Binali*

Yildirim University; Cennet Engin, Middle East Technical University

Breaking the Sentence: Storytelling in prisoner-authored newsletters as critical pedagogy. *Alexis Carr, Simon Fraser University; Sacha Alfonso V., University of Ottawa*

From Remembering to Repositioning: A Returning Youth's Language of Memory, Belonging, and Future Possibility. *Fatemeh Mozaffari, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Noemi Waight, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Ryan M. Rish, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Jennifer Tripp, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Stacy Scheuneman, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Finn Goehrig, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

Data and Farming: Uncovering Tensions in Food Justice. *Marc Sager, Southern Methodist University; Maximilian Sherard, University of North Texas; Anthony J. Petrosino, Southern Methodist University*

Chair: *Diane L. Schallert, University of Texas at Austin*

Discussant: *Nisha Acharya Julien, Opportunity Consulting*

75.022. Generative AI and Academic Writing: Studies from Diverse Contexts. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Symposium
Westin Bonaventure, Level 2, Mt. Washington; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Beginning with the end in mind: Using generative AI in undergraduate STEM writing instruction. *Tamara Powell Tate, University of California - Irvine*

From Adoption to Adaptation: Generative AI in Middle School ELA. *Daniel Ritchie, University of California - Irvine; Dana Saito-Stehberger, University of California - Irvine*

Rethinking Writing Support: AI as Peer, Editor, and Partner in the Undergraduate Classroom. *Maura White, University of California - San Diego*

Generative AI meets the heritage bilingual: A classroom-based study on writing feedback. *Julio Torres, University of California - Irvine*

Chair: *Mark Warschauer, University of California - Irvine*

Discussant: *Tanya Baker, National Writing Project*

75.023. Motivation and Identity in Engineering Education: Pathways from Childhood to University. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Santa Barbara C; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

"I Want to Change the World": Young Learners Explore Biomedical Engineering Through Hands-On Engineering Design Activities. *Zahra Baradaran Shoraka, University of Iowa; Kay Ellen Ramey, University of Iowa*

Pathways to Engineering: How Secondary School Students Perceive and Construct Engineering Identity. *Elizabeth Adelman, FHI 360; Caitlin Kim, FHI 360; Rachel Hatch, FHI 360; Caitlin Dailey; Ying Wang, FHI 360*

Uncovering Engineering Pathways Through the Eyes of Counselors Using a Photovoice Approach. *Shukufe Rahman, The Ohio State University; Junzhao Wang, Arizona State University; Adam R. Carberry, The Ohio State University; Medha Dalal, Arizona State University*

Visualizing Equity: The Motivational Impact of Place-Based Data Use in Systems Engineering Classrooms. *Ian Thacker, University of Texas - San Antonio; Francisco Benita, Tecnológico de Monterrey*

Chair: *James L Huff, University of Georgia*

75.024. Out-of-school Learning: Engaging Communities and High-Impact Practices. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, La Cienega; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Challenges of Museum Educators in Navigating School Partnerships: Multiple Case Studies. *Moch. Nurfahrul Lukmanul Khakim, -*

Cultivating Community through Gardening: A YPAR Project on Greenhouses. *Kayeon Koh, University of California - Los Angeles; Victoria Arali Daniels, University of California - Los Angeles; Mariana Gudino Avalos, University of California - Los Angeles; Christine Lee, University of California - Los Angeles*

Harnessing the Horse: Student Perceptions of Equine Focused High-Impact Practices. *Casie S. Bass, Purdue University*
Outdoor Field Trips as a Pedagogy for Deeper Learning. *Katherine Ashton, University of Oklahoma*

Student Engagement Across Different Inquiry Tasks in GPS-Supported Outdoor Learning: From the ICAP Perspective. *Miao Yue, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Morris Siu-Yung Jong, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Yuting Chen, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Chin-Chung Tsai, National Taiwan Normal University*

Chair: *Christine Lee, University of California - Los Angeles*

75.025. Arts-Based Approaches for Expanding Methodological Terrain. Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Paper Session
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 6th Floor, Metropolitan; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Liberating Research: Using Art-based Methods with Undocumented and Immigration-Impacted Students. *Laura E. Enriquez, University of California - Irvine; Giovanna Itzel, University of California - Irvine*

Painting Data and Visualizing Voice: Rural Educators' Narratives of Newcomer English Learner Support. *Riya Chakraborty, University of Florida*

Pardon My MESI Work: Musically Enhanced Self-Inquiry as a Creative, Reflexive, Critical, and Multimodal Methodology. *Naomi Ramirez, San Diego State University*

Photovoice in Higher Education: Examining College Students Academic and Professional Lived Experiences. *Megan Lapkoff, Clemson University; D. Matthew Boyer, Clemson University; Kelly Lazar, Clemson University; Taneisha Brown, Transformative Research & Evaluation*
Chair: *Kelly Clark/Keefe, University of Vermont*

75.026. Division D Mentoring Session. Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Workshop
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Wilshire Grand Ballroom II; 11:45am to 1:15pm
Chair: *Lei Jiang, University of Kansas*

75.027. Cross-Cutting Research on Risk and Resilience Factors Among LGBTQIA+ Individuals. Division E - Counseling and Human Development; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 301A; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Trajectories and Predictors of Bias-Based Bullying Victimization Among Transgender and Nonbinary Youth. *Melissa K. Holt, Boston University; Katharine Parodi, Boston University; Andra Preda, Boston University; Nicolina Fusco, Boston University; Alyssa Marie Ciniglio, Boston University; Aidan D. Kraus, Boston University; Jennifer Greif Green, Boston University*

Hidden Patterns, Lasting Effects: Violence Victimization and Perpetration Typologies and Longitudinal Implications in LGBTQ+ Adolescents. *Yinuo Xu, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Yutong Gao, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Dorothy L. Espelage, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*

A Qualitative Thematic Analysis of Mentors and Role Models Among Transgender and Nonbinary Youth. *Katharine Parodi, Boston University; Melissa K. Holt, Boston University; Mario Crown, Boston University; Sharada Krishnan, Boston University; Andra Preda, Boston University*

Beyond Diagnostic Categories: Examining the Interplay of Autism, Gender, and Social Context in Mental Health. *Shalini Sivathasan, Boston College; Chang Gu, Boston College; Samantha Martin, Boston College; Amy Hartman, University of Pittsburgh*

Chairs: *Katharine Parodi, Boston University; Melissa K. Holt, Boston University*

Discussant: *Jennifer Greif Green, Boston University*

75.028. Building Abolitionist Futures in Education Now: Critical Engagements with Freedom, Belonging, and Police-Free Schools. Division G - Social Context of Education; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 504; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Whose Compliance Matters? Incarcerated youth identify prison geographies, and possibilities for abolition. *Subini Ancy Anamma, Stanford University*

Abolitionist Possibilities in Education Research: Methodological Praxis with Black Foster Youth. *Brianna Marche' Harvey, California State University - Fullerton*
The productive tensions of designing, implementing and negotiating an abolitionist vision of police-free schools. *Rekia G. Jibrin, University of California - Santa Cruz*
From Mandated Reporters to Mandated Supporters: Educators Rebuilding Safety to Challenge the Family Policing System. *Erica R. Meiners, Northeastern Illinois University*

Chair: *Subini Ancy Anamma, Stanford University*

Discussant: *Michelle Fine, Graduate Center - CUNY*

75.029. Communities of Resistance and Dissent, Aztlán-Anáhuac-Ixtepec, Gran México--Part 1: Critical, Local, Transnational Teachers and Teacher Education. Division G - Social Context of Education; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 301B; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Science Improvisations: Reconstructing the Past Through a Sense of Belonging. *Zulema Williams, University of Texas - Rio Grande Valley*

My Journey as an Elementary Science Teacher: From Linear to Authentic Criticalities. *Johanna Lynn Esparza, University of Texas - Rio Grande Valley*

Las Fronterizas: Transnational Students Teaching U. S. history in Transnational-Local spaces. *Raul Garza, University of Texas - Rio Grande Valley*

Borderlands of Science Education A Critical Curricular Praxis for Community Health and Healing. *Miriam M. Ortiz, University of Texas - Rio Grande Valley*

Chairs: *Ana Laura Gallardo Gutiérrez, National Autonomous University of Mexico; Gabriel Vega Torres, Universidad Pedagógica Nacional Ixtepec*

Discussant: *James C. Jupp, University of Texas - Rio Grande Valley*

75.030. Divison G VP Grad Student Early Career Poster Session. Division G - Social Context of Education; Structured Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 515B; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

1. Queer Narrative Inquiry as a Tool for Social Justice in Education (Poster 1). *Jeffery Franklin, Indiana University - Indianapolis*
2. Social Studies Preservice Teachers' Discussions and the Problem of Context (Poster 2). *Andrew J. Schiera, University of Colorado - Boulder; Zander Nowell, University of Colorado - Boulder*
3. Of Math and Men (Poster 3). *Antwuan Williams, Wayne State*

University

4. Visualizing Methodological Possibilities with and for Latinx Communities in Education (Poster 4). *Gabriel Rodríguez Lemus, University of Texas at Austin*
 5. Building Family Partnerships through Home Visits: Dual Capacity-Building Meets Pacific Islander Relational Reciprocity (Poster 5). *Roberto Jacob Laanan, University of Utah*
 6. Queering Methodology in Educational Leadership: Critical Narrative Analysis and Generative AI for Structural Analysis (Poster 6). *Luis Alberto Legaspi, University of San Diego*
 7. How Mixed-Race People with Two or More Identities of Color Experience Unhooking from Whiteness (Poster 7). *Josh Manlove, Indiana University - Indianapolis*
 8. The Multiple Worlds of Queer Black Girls (Poster 8). *Kristina Johnson-Yates, Indiana University - Indianapolis*
 9. “These Kids Are Ruthless With Their Politics”: Preservice Teachers’ Perspectives on Navigating Controversial Conversations (Poster 9). *Anda Grace Pearson, Utah State University; Edgar Díaz, Utah State University*
 10. Inclusion as a Form of Surveillance (Poster 10). *Rebecca Brown, Wayne State University*
 11. The Critical Role of Middle Managers in Resisting Backlash at HSIs (Poster 11). *Arturo Anaya Servin, University of San Diego*
 12. Student Meaning-making About the Purposes of Schooling in the Rio Grande Valley of South Texas (Poster 12). *Alejandro Madrigal, University of Texas at Austin*
- Chair: *Cleveland Hayes, Indiana University - Indianapolis*

75.031. Enduring Erasures, Radical Futures: Black Males' Survival in Education. Division G - Social Context of Education; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 501B;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

- Black Boys Matter in the Future We Imagine: Centering Teacher Relationships and Culturally Relevant Pedagogy. *Sofina Shekhar, University of Delaware; Roderick L. Carey, University of Delaware; Lauren M Strickland, University of Delaware; Tia Navelene Barnes, University of Delaware*
- Contextualizing Black Men Teacher Retention Using Researcher Reflexivity of Social Media Data and Peer Interviews. *William N. Thomas, American University*
- Resilience Without Reform: Black Male Faculty and the Structural Toll of Academic Survival. *Darryl Corey, Radford University; Edwin Nii Bonney, Clemson University*
- What Do You Tell a Black Athlete After They Were Called the N-Word? Teaching Through the Unanswerable in the American South. *Jaquial Durham, Clemson University*
- Chair: *Travis J. Bristol, University of California - Berkeley*
Discussant: *Roderick L. Carey, University of Delaware*

75.032. Parenting as Praxis: Families, Schooling, and the Quest for Racial, Linguistic, and Disability Justice. Division G - Social Context of Education; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304C;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

- Beyond Problem, Right, and Resource: Transnational Family Language Policy and Language Racialization Across Borders. *Vania Ledesma, University of Texas at Austin*
- Mitigating Attrition in Educational Pathways Through Transformative Parent Engagement. *Monique Escobedo, San Diego State University; Cristina Alfaro, San Diego State University; Velia Huerta, San Diego State University; Saul I. Maldonado, San Diego State University*
- Unforgetting the Families Who Built Special Education: Computational Analysis of IEP Language and Family Voice. *Antoinette Banks, University of California - Davis*
- Parenting as Racialized Educational Practice: Strategic Adaptation and Cultivation in an Asian American Community. *Christopher Hu, University of Alabama*
- Chair: *Antoinette Banks, University of California - Davis*
Discussant: *Jing Su, University of California - Santa Barbara*

75.033. Placing Blackness: An exploration of Black STEM students' connections to place identity. Division G - Social Context of Education; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 303A;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

- Comin' from where I'm from: Connecting place and Blackness in students' STEM major experiences. *Nickolaus A. Ortiz, Georgia State University; Paris Iyamu, Georgia State University*
- Spaces as buffers: A spatial analysis of Black undergraduate STEM student experiences. *Tia C. Madkins, The University of Texas at Austin; Terrell R Morton, University of Illinois at Chicago; Yasmiyn Irizarry, University of Texas at Austin; Nkasano R. Fullerton, University of Texas at Austin*
- The Multidimensionality of place in informing Black students' STEM engagement. *Shari E. Watkins, American University; Terrell R Morton, University of Illinois at Chicago; Brian McGowan, American University*
- Not Just for me: Diasporic duty, Black spatiality, and STEM as collective aspiration for international Black students. *Joanna N. Ali, North Carolina State University; Paula Groves Price, North Carolina A&T State University*
- Chair: *Andrea Tyler*
Discussants: *Kaleb Germinaro, University of Illinois at Chicago; Ashley N. Woodson, Black epiSTEMologies*

75.034. Sustaining Agency Across Social Contexts: How Young Children and their Communities are Reclaiming Agency. Division G - Social Context of Education; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304A;

11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

“So You Know You're Not Alone”: Mutual Responsibility Among Children and Adults on Tribal Land. *Jennifer Keys Adair, The University of Texas at Austin; Monica Alonzo, University of Texas at Austin*

Sacred Boundaries, Structured Agency: Reframing Inquiry in a Jewish Reggio-Inspired Classroom. *Shubhi Sachdeva, San Francisco State University; Molly E. McManus, San Francisco State University*

“Uh-Uh, I don't go for that!” Young Disabled Children of Color Subverting Schooling's Carceral Logics. *Soyoung Park, Bank Street College of Education; Natacha Ndabahaganye Jones, University of North Texas*

Young Children of Color's Agency and Creativity as Pathways to Imagining New Visions and Futures. *Sunmin Lee, Texas State University; Kiyomi Sanchez-Suzuki Colegrove, Texas State University; Amber T. Fowler, University of Texas at Austin*

Chair: *Haeny S. Yoon, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Discussant: *Haeny S. Yoon, Teachers College, Columbia University*

75.035. Data-Driven Approaches to Supporting Striving Learners in the Post-Pandemic Era. Division H - Research, Evaluation and Assessment in Schools; Symposium

InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Los Feliz; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

State of Student Learning in 2025. *Kelsey Young, Curriculum Associates; Ethan Young, Curriculum Associates*

Meeting Readers Where They Are: Personalized Instructional Support for Grade 1-5 Striving Readers. *Juno Yingzhi Dong, University of California - Los Angeles; Lauren Stargel, Curriculum Associates*

Curriculum Matters: Math Growth Among Low-Performing Elementary Students in Grades 3-5. *Preston Martin, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Gregory King, Curriculum Associates*

Chairs: *Gregory King, Curriculum Associates; Lauren Stargel, Curriculum Associates*

Discussant: *Morgan S. Polikoff, University of Southern California*

75.036. Global Contexts for Research-Practice Partnerships: They Come in All Shapes and Sizes. Division H - Research, Evaluation and Assessment in Schools; Structured Poster Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 515A; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

1. Research Practice Partnerships in Rural Places: A View from New York State (Poster 1). *Kristen C. Wilcox, University at Albany - SUNY; Maria I Khan, University at Albany - SUNY;*

Paul Guay, University at Albany - SUNY

2. A ‘Train-The-Trainees’ Model for Organizational Learning: Identifying Factors for Success Across Levels (Poster 2). *Kirsti Klette, University of Oslo; Inga Staal Jensen, University of Oslo, Norway*

3. The Impact of Systemic Factors on Research-Practice Partnerships: Insights from Israel (Poster 3). *Linor Lea Hadar, University of Haifa; Hadar Baharav, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev*

4. Tracing Boundary Objects and Project Mobility: A Case Study from Singapore (Poster 4). *Dennis Kwek, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University; Chin Ee Loh, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University; Lorraine Ow, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University*

5. Bridging Research, Practice, and Community: A Holistic Model for Play-Based Learning in Early Childhood Education (Poster 5). *Alan C. K. Cheung, The Chinese University of Hong Kong*

6. Stockholm Teaching & Learning Studies as a Research-Practice Partnership: A Case Study from Sweden (Poster 6). *Simon Sjölund, Mälardalen University*

Chairs: *Kristen C. Wilcox, University at Albany - SUNY; Chin Ee Loh, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University*

75.037. Artificial Intelligence in Action: Transforming Assessments. Division I - Education in the Professions; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 1; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

AI-Based Assessment of Nursing Students' Head-to-Toe Physical Assessment Performance: Video Segmentation and Classification. *Ikseon Choi, Emory University; Sarah E Finch, Emory University; Sejung Kwon, Emory University; Jongwon Kim, Emory University; Autherine Abiri, Emory University; Elizabeth Zarantonello, Emory University; Christine Nguyen, Emory University; Rose Hayes, Emory University; Laika Steiger, Emory University; Beth Ann Swan, Emory University*

AI-based Formative Assessments in Medical Education: Insight and Challenges. *Xiaomei Song, Case Western Reserve University*

Integrative review of Qualitative studies on AI-powered Clinical Decision Support Systems: For a more Care-Attuned Health Profession Education. *Ahreum Lim, Arizona State University; Nathaniel Kim, University of Arizona; Brian Christopher Gin, University of Illinois at Chicago*

Pre-Annotation of Student Questions in OSCE Transcripts: A Good First Try. *Scott Mandel, National Board of Medical Examiners; Janet Mee, NBME; Tazin Afrin, National Board of Medical Examiners; Thai Quang Ong, National Board of Medical Examiners*

Chair: *Taiwo Feyijimi, University of Georgia*
Discussant: *Anita Samuel, Uniformed Services University of the Health Sciences*

75.038. Holistic Success: Institutional Influences on Community College Student Outcomes. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum F; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Conditional Momentum? Mental Health, Academic Progress, and Core Competencies Among STEM Community College Students. *Xiwei Zhu, San Diego State University; Xueli Wang, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Aikebaier Nadila, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Reimagining Access: The Community College Baccalaureate as a Pathway to Equity and Graduate School Aspirations. *Adrian H. Huerta, University of Southern California; Cecilia Rios-Aguilar, University of California - Los Angeles; Marcela G. Cuellar, University of California - Davis; Jessica Leila Carranza, University of Southern California; Jose Bermejo, University of Southern California; Michael Corvera, University of Southern California; Davis Vo, University of California - Los Angeles*

Returning California Community College Student Outcomes in the wake of AB 705. *Taylor Stenley, Research for Action; Mark Duffly, Research for Action; Dae Y. Kim, Research for Action*

Success in community college transfer-level math: Using multi-level modeling to explore variation between instructors. *Daniela R. Amaya, University of California - Los Angeles; Cecilia Rios-Aguilar, University of California - Los Angeles*

Refugee Belonging in U.S. Higher Education: A Critical Integration Studies Approach. *Ishara Casellas Connors, Texas A&M University; Kerri Evans, University of Maryland - Baltimore County; Lisa Unangst, SUNY - Empire State University*

75.039. Constructing Futures with Technology: Digital Literacies, AI Integration, and Transformative Teacher Preparation. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 9; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Fostering Pre-service Teachers' Data Literacy through Inquiry-based Learning in a Technology Integration Course. *Wen Wen, SUNY Oneonta*

Fostering Teacher AI Competency Development from a Systematic Review across Micro, Meso, and Macro Systems. *Xinyan Zhou, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Thomas K.F. Chiu, The Chinese University of Hong Kong*

Navigating Social Studies Lesson Planning with Generative AI: Exploring Pre-Service Teachers' Agency and Critical Digital

Pedagogical Practices. *Anna Eunji Kim, Pennsylvania State University; Suyoung Park, The Pennsylvania State University; Seunghoon Han, University of Northern Iowa*
Preservice Teachers Learning Computational and Digital Literacies: The Realities of Connecting Theory and Practice. *Michelle C. Fraboni, Queens College - CUNY*
Shifting Minds or Reinforcing Myths? Empirical Insights into AI-related Affective Changes Among Future Technology Teachers. *Mats Vernholz, Paderborn University; Johannes Schäfers, Paderborn University; Gabriela Jonas-Ahrend, Paderborn University; Katrin Temmen, Paderborn University*

Chair: *Keirah Comstock, University of Rochester*

Discussant: *Ann Marie Ryan, University of Texas - San Antonio*

75.040. Voices of Emotional First Responders: Honoring Teacher Humanity Through Trauma and Overlapping Crises. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 7; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Breathing Through the Smoke?: A Critical Narrative of Teaching and Grieving in the Wake of Crisis. *Jensine Magaly Lucas, Pepperdine University; Cristina M. Arellano, Santa Monica-Malibu Unified School District*

Reimagining Teacher Education: Embedding Trauma-Informed Practices and Mental Health Supports Post-Crisis. *Ellin Avanesian, Pepperdine University; Elianna Campos, Pasadena Unified*

Echoes of Loss: Delayed Grief and Its Impact on Teacher Well-Being. *Jensine Magaly Lucas, Pepperdine University; Ellin Avanesian, Pepperdine University; Cristina M. Arellano, Santa Monica-Malibu Unified School District; Elianna Campos, Pasadena Unified*

Chair: *Anthony Collatos, Pepperdine University*

Discussant: *Anthony Collatos, Pepperdine University*

75.041. You're Speaking My Language: Critical Perspectives on Identity, Equity, and Professional Learning to Support Multilingual Learners. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 8; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Helping Overwhelmed Teachers Become Empowered: Language Teacher Educators Leading Professional Development in NYS Standards Reform. *SeyyedeH Mobina Hosseini, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Erin Kearney, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

Longitudinal Impact of the Advanced Dual-Certificate Professional Development Project: Emerging Leaders for Diverse Schools. *Gulnur Ozbek, St. John's University; John Spiridakis, St. John's University; Seokhee Cho, St. John's*

University; Audrey Figueroa Murphy, St. John's University; Jordan Gonzalez, St. John's University; Yvonne Pratt-Johnson, Saint John's University; Stephen Kotok, St. John's University

Mobilizing Intersectional Teacher Identity Work in Professional Development for Secondary Teachers of Emergent Bilinguals. *Jerry Romero, University of Texas - San Antonio; Bedrettin Yazan, University of Texas - San Antonio; Caryn M. Calisi, University of Texas at San Antonio; Jorge L. Solis, University of Texas - San Antonio; Kristen Lindahl, University of Texas - San Antonio; MICHAEL MAURICIO, University of Texas - San Antonio; Amanda de Oliveira Silva, University of Texas - San Antonio; Gilberto P. Lara, University of Texas - San Antonio*

Chair: *Jennifer M. Collett, Lehman College - CUNY*

Discussant: *Deborah D. Dailey, University of Central Arkansas*

75.042. Unforgetting Methods: Reimagining Policy Analysis for Complex Educational Futures. Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 10; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Beyond Patton and Bardach: Creating a Unified Framework for Policy Analysis. *Tasnim Ziad Altamimi, University of North Carolina - Greensboro; Sandra Ayoo, University of North Carolina - Greensboro*

ICT Policy-Praxis: Empowering Teachers in Inclusive Policymaking. *Thirusellvan Vandeyar, University of Pretoria; Saloshna Vandeyar, University of Pretoria*

Some Assembly Required: Customizing CFIR for Educational Research. *Stephanie L. Brown, Florida State University; Dinara Ibrayeva, Florida State University; Zahra Gholami, Florida State University; Leah Register, Florida State University; Latara O. Lampkin, Heritage University; Alexandria Thomas, Florida State University*

The Components Approach: Addressing Teacher Shortages Through Targeted Policy Implementation. *Etai Mizrav, Northeastern University*

Unpacking the Latent Clusters of Equity Indicators via Correspondence Analysis Using Open School Equity Data. *Alex J. Bowers, Teachers College, Columbia University; Guoliang Xu, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Chair: *Jacquelyn Williams, Clemson University*

Discussant: *Alison Wilson, University of Houston*

SIG Sessions

75.043. Artificial Intelligence as a Catalyst for Transforming Accreditation in Educator Preparation. SIG-Accreditation, Assessment, and Program Evaluation in Education Preparation; Symposium
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor,

Wilshire Grand Ballroom I; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Introduction to AI Tools in Accreditation. *Anne Renee Tapp Jakska, Saginaw Valley State University*

Ethical Implications Using the FATE Framework. *Malina Monaco, Council for the Accreditation of Educator Preparation*

AI for Continuous Improvement and Equity. *Beth W. Kubitskey, Eastern Michigan University*

Emerging Trends and Agile Accreditation Systems. *Malina Monaco, Council for the Accreditation of Educator Preparation*

Chair: *Malina Monaco, Council for the Accreditation of Educator Preparation*

Discussant: *Anne Renee Tapp Jakska, Saginaw Valley State University*

75.044. (Re)searching to (re)imagine: Futuring through critical arts based methods. SIG-Arts-Based Educational Research; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 309; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Improvising and Persisting (IP): A Mentoring Model. *Vonzell Agosto, University of South Florida; Deirdre Cobb-Roberts, University of South Florida; Lauren Braunstein, University of South Florida; Maria Migueliz Valcarlos, Eastern New Mexico University*

Stagecrafting Change: Socio-Politically Conscious Professional Development for Science Educators. *Tara M. Nkrumah, Arizona State University; Elaine Arrieta Bohn, Arizona State University*

Becoming (Re)searchers: Unpacking Researcher-Participant Power Dynamics through Critical Arts-Based Methods. *LaSonja Roberts, Western Michigan University; Regina L. Garza Mitchell, Western Michigan University; Beixi Li, Western Michigan University; LaRonda Moore, Western Michigan University*

Chair: *Amanda O. Latz, Ball State University*

Discussant: *Charles F. Vanover, University of South Florida*

75.045. Translanguaging in Five Heritage Language Learning Spaces: Challenges and Affordances for Both Teachers and Learners. SIG-Bilingual Education Research; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 505; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Dismantling Existing Language Hierarchy and Enhancing Heritage Language Attitudes Amongst Ontario's Immigrant Youths Through Translanguaging. *Sudhashree Girmohanta, University of Toronto - OISE*

Cultivating Translanguaging Space: Teachers' Stance, Pedagogical Design, and Students' Agency in a Three-Year

Ethnography. *Jiadi Zhang, University of Missouri - St. Louis*
Teacher Ideologies and Transdialecting Pedagogies in an
Arabic Heritage Community School. *Yousra Abourehab,*
University of Arizona

Creating a Hybrid Learning Space Through Translanguaging in
a Heritage Language Classroom for Korean-American
Students. *Chaehyun Lee, Southeastern Oklahoma State*
University

“I feel weird when I speak हिन्दी ...”: Translanguaging,
resistance, and multimodality in elementary classrooms.
Harini Rajagopal, University of British Columbia

Chairs: *Sudhashree Girmohanta, University of Toronto - OISE;*
Jiadi Zhang, University of Missouri - St. Louis

Discussant: *Shakina Rajendram, University of Toronto*

75.046. Unforgetting Stories in Education and Reimagining the

**Future: Intersections of (Auto)biography, Learning,
Teaching, and Empowerment.** SIG-Biographical and
Documentary Research; Paper Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 306A;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Unforgetting Teaching Herstories: Bringing Relationship
Literacies Forward While Shifting Narratives About
Teaching Through Life Stories. *Marissa Schweinfurth,*
University of Northern Iowa; Bianca J. Nightengale-Lee,
Western Michigan University; Margaret-Mary Sulentic
Dowell, Louisiana State University; Corey Drake, The Math
Learning Center; Margaret Vaughn, Washington State
University; Lori Ann Norton-Meier, University of Northern
Iowa; Erin Summerhays, University of Northern Iowa

Patriarchal Learning Environment: A Biographical Study.
Nelofar Khamisani, Kansas State University

Journeying South: Museums, Educators, and Untold Histories
of the Mississippi Delta. *Lori M. West, Knox College*

Digital Trans-Literacies for Empowerment: Negotiating In-
betweenness in Hong Kong EMI Classrooms. *John Chi Kin*
Lee, The Education University of Hong Kong; Yu Xiang, The
Education University of Hong Kong; Michelle Mingyue Gu,
Education University of Hong Kong

Reimagining the Future of Teaching With Black and Brown
Male Educators. *Valentina Alpuin, University of Illinois at*
Chicago; Decoteau J. Irby, University of Illinois at Chicago;
Ceily Moore, University of Illinois at Chicago; Jeniece M.
Fleming, University of Illinois at Chicago; Duane Bernard
Davis, University of Chicago

Chair: *Lori Ann Norton-Meier, University of Northern Iowa*

Discussants: *Patience Amadu, University of Colorado - Colorado*
Springs; Zheng Ma, University of Toronto - OISE; Tarek
ElBaba, Dar Al Fikr Schools

75.047. Race, Rurality, and Education: Envisioning Educational Equity in Racialized Rural Spaces. SIG- Critical Examination of Race, Ethnicity, Class and Gender in

Education; Symposium

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum
B; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Imagining the Rural: Political Economy and Racialized
Representations of Rurality in Education and Social
Research. *Rachelle Kuehl, Virginia Tech; Zeus Leonardo,*
University of California - Berkeley

The First Morrill Act and Agricultural Settler Conquest: The
Case of the University of California. *Rosalie Zdzienicka*
Fanshel, University of California - Berkeley

Fighting Back: School Closure and Resistance in the Rural
Black South. *Mara C. Tieken, Bates College*

The Multi-Scalar (De)Construction of Rural Latinidad and
College (In)Opportunities in California's San Joaquin
Valley. *Mayra Puente, University of California - Santa*
Barbara

Chair: *Joyce E. King, Georgia State University*

Discussant: *Zeus Leonardo, University of California - Berkeley*

75.048. Centering Other Epistemologies in Critical

Curriculum Studies. SIG-Critical Issues in Curriculum and
Cultural Studies; Paper Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 303B;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Afro-Mexican epistemologies in education: material justice as
the basis for ethnic and intersectionality justice for education
in the U.S. *Raul Olmo Fregoso Bailón, University of Nevada*
- Reno

Cosmic Pedagogy Meets Machine Logic: K-12 Teachers as
Organic Intellectuals in the Era of Generative AI. *Hilda*
Yaneth Sotelo, University of Texas - El Paso

Rooted in Place: Building Curriculum Through Rural
Relationships and Reflexive Inquiry. *Alycia M. Elfreich,*
Montana State University; Leslie Ann Rogers, Montana State
University

Scripted to Teach: A Critical Discourse Analysis of Scripted
Curricula in Science Education. *Dilara Kara Zorluoglu,*
University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Debika Jana, University
of Nevada - Las Vegas; Adrienne Dizon, University of
Nevada - Las Vegas; Ambreen Islam, University of Nevada -
Las Vegas; Katherine Wade-Jaimes, University of Nevada -
Las Vegas; Sameul Hoque Fahad, University of Nevada -
Las Vegas; Chike Elue, University of Nevada - Las Vegas;
Burak Sahin, University of Nevada - Las Vegas

Theorizing self, other, and community: Weaving Korean
Epistemologies with Pulzip [Grass Straw] Art. *Seungho*
Moon, Loyola University Chicago; Yeorim Ana Hwang,
Oklahoma State University

Chair: *Gabriela López, Stanford University*

Discussant: *Astri Napitupulu, University of Missouri - St. Louis*

75.049. Affective, Ecological, and Technological

Entanglements in Education. SIG-Critical Posthuman and Postfoundational Studies in Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum A; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

A Meteorology of Learning: Affective Violence at American Settler Universities. *Vandhana Ravi, University of California - San Diego*

Black Technological Thought in the Civil Rights Era. *Anabella Afra Boateng, New York University*

Breaking down binaries between formal and nonformal learning for preservice teachers. *Leah Master, New York University*

Reconfiguring Teacher Learning With GenAI: An Onto-Epistemological Framework for AI Integration in STEM Education. *Sophia Jeong, The Ohio State University; Sevil Akaygun, Bogazici University; Mutlu Sen-Akbulut, Bogazici University; Ulku Seher Budak, Bogazici University*

Chair: *Kathryn J. Strom, California State University - East Bay*

Discussant: *Oona Fontanella-Nothom, California State University - Dominguez Hills*

75.050. Civic Histories: Learning the Past, Understanding the Present, Possibilizing the Future. SIG-Democratic Citizenship in Education; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 6; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

How the Past is Produced: Teaching Critical Historiographies for Civic Possibilities. *Liz Harrelson Magill, Baylor University*

Enacting Civic Histories: Instructional Decision Making and Connecting the Past to the Present. *Andrew del Calvo, Rutgers University - New Brunswick; Kira Roberson, School District of Philadelphia*

“We get to live as historians”: Analyzing housework’s past and present with upper elementary students. *Alexandra Thrall, Baylor University; Liz Harrelson Magill, Baylor University; T. Philip Nichols, Baylor University*

Investigating Teachers’ Beliefs About Presentism. *James Miles, University of Alberta; Lindsay S. Gibson, University of British Columbia*

Chair: *Andrew del Calvo, Rutgers University - New Brunswick*

Discussant: *Joseph E. Kahne, University of California - Riverside*

75.051. Intersectional Disability Justice Critical Autoethnographic Counter-Histories as Living Archive. SIG-Disability Studies in Education; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 511AB; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Disability Justice in the Shadows: The Unseen Labors of Black Sibling Caregivers. *Ayana Cheyenne Colvin, University of Pennsylvania*

Interrogating “American dream”: A Critical Autoethnography

of a Disabled Immigrant. *Miso Kwak, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Removed for Protection: A Critical Autoethnography of Schooling, Space, and Relational Pedagogy. *Samantha Marie Jacob, University of Wisconsin-Madison*

Brokering Belonging: A Duoethnography of Sisterhood, Stigma, and Siblinghood Across Borders. *Jane Y. Jeong, University of Texas at Austin; Minji Lee, Ewha Womans University*

Advocating for Belonging for Transnational and Multilingual Learners with/out Dis/Abilities: Critical Autoethnography. *Monaliza M Chian, University of Northern Iowa*

Hypocritical Gatekeepers Accept Accountability as "Ideological Gatekeepers" for Black Dis/Abled Females, "Praxis What You Teach." *Shariese Katrell, Rowan University*

Chair: *Suman Rath, Montclair State University*

Discussant: *David I. Hernandez-Saca, University of Northern Iowa*

75.052. Relevance of Individual and Family Environment Factors for Young Children’s Language Use and Language Skills. SIG-Early Education and Child Development; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Georgia I; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

The Role of Parental Acculturation in Immigrant Families’ Language Interactions at Home. *Maria Belen Buttler, University of California - Davis; Qing Zhou, University of California - Berkeley; Yuuko Uchikoshi, University of California - Davis*

Mother, Father, and Child Code Switching and Links to Child Language Development. *Amy Pace, University of Washington; Ines Juhee Sohn, University of Washington; Sara Kover, University of Washington; Bonnie Lau, University of Washington*

The Impact of Home Language, SES, and Shared Reading Practices for First-Graders’ Grammatical Skills. *Svenja Wehrhöfer, TU Dortmund University; Leonie Dargiewicz, Technische Universität Dortmund; Fani Lauermann, University of Bonn; Ulrich Ludewig, TU Dortmund University; Nele McElvany, TU Dortmund University; Annika Öhle-Peters, TU Dortmund University*

The Benefits of Reading Digital Storybooks with Animations Among Low-Income Preschoolers. *Claire Seung-Hee Son, University of Utah*

Chair: *Svenja Wehrhöfer, TU Dortmund University*
Discussant: *Molly F. Collins, Vanderbilt University*

75.053. Innovative Statistical Methods and Computational Tools for Complex Research Designs. SIG-Educational Statisticians; Paper Session
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 7th Floor,

Hollywood Ballroom I; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

- Designing Feasible Optimal Treatment Regimes for Personalized Education. *Yuxuan Li, Teachers College, Columbia University; Chenguang Pan, Teachers College, Columbia University; Youmi Suk, Teachers College, Columbia University*
- Estimating Marginal Effects for Zero-inflated Models: Introducing the R package *mzim*. *Chendong Li, Texas A&M University; Oiman Kwok, Texas A&M University*
- Robustness of nMAX for Sample Size Planning Under Nonnormality. *Gregory R. Hancock, University of Maryland; Yi Feng, University of California - Los Angeles*
- Evaluating Subject Mobility in Partial Nesting Contexts: Multiple Membership Partially Nested Models. *Yara Al-nouri, Georgia Institute of Technology; Audrey J. Leroux, Georgia Institute of Technology*
- AI-Based Evaluation of Intervention Effects in Single-Case Designs: A Study of Claude's Analytical Capacity. *Isaac Akuoko-Mensah, University of Nevada - Reno; Li-Ting Chen, University of Nevada - Reno*

Chair: *Liu Liu, University of Georgia*

75.054. Decolonizing Environmental Education: Place, Pedagogy, and Counter-Histories. SIG-Environmental Education; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 306B;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

- From Water Pollution to Water Protectors: Teacher Reflections on a K-5 EcoJustice Curriculum. *Marissa E Bellino, The College of New Jersey; Greer Burroughs, The College of New Jersey*
- 'Ike 'Aina: Ecological Presence as a Framework for Environmental Science Education Examined Across Two Curricula in Rural Hawaii. *Tyler Hansen, Utah State University*
- Unforgetting Histories: Narrative Inquiry on Encounters with the Amazonian Territory in Brazil. *Audrey Dahl, Université du Québec à Montréal; Inny Accioly, Universidade Federal Fluminense*
- Folded Futures: The Exquisite Corpse of Citizenship and the Emergence of Planetizen. *Victoria Desimoni, Arizona State University; Iveta Silova, Arizona State University; Rūta Gajauskaitė, Vilnius University; Dilraba Anayatova, Arizona State University*

Discussant: *Amelia Lynn King-Kostelac, University of Texas - San Antonio*

75.055. I ulu no ka lālā i ke kumu: Grounded histories, growing thriving communities, schools and families. SIG-Family, School, Community Partnerships; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum I;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

- He lei pōina 'ole ke keiki: Weaving pilina, connections and aloha. *Dawn Rego-Yee, Ceeds of Peace*
- Title: Ka wā ma mua, ka wā ma hope ('Ōlelo No'eau #6) The past is in the future. Culture-based and trauma informed SEL in community schools. *Sarah Rice, University of Hawaii - Hilo*
- He 'a'ali'i kū makani mai au; 'a'ohe makani nana e kula'i: Caring for our 'a'ali'i--The critical role of teacher climate in community schools. *Margary Martin, University of Hawaii'i at Hilo*

Chair: *Margary Martin, University of Hawaii'i at Hilo*

Discussant: *Jessica Shiller, Towson University*

75.056. Costing Education: Evidence-Based Approaches to Equity and Adequacy in School Finance. SIG-Fiscal Issues, Policy and Education Finance; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum H; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

- Centering Equity for English Language Learners: A Multi-Measure School Finance Analysis in Wisconsin. *Xinyu Guan, University of Wisconsin - Madison*
- Determining Equitable Funding Levels for California Community Colleges: A Cost Function Approach. *Jesse D. Levin, American Institutes for Research; Bruce D. Baker, University of Miami; Christopher Brooks, American Institutes for Research*
- Understanding the Cost of Providing Adequate Educational Opportunity in Oregon. *Jesse D. Levin, American Institutes for Research; Bruce D. Baker, University of Miami; Christopher Brooks, American Institutes for Research; Brad Salvato, American Institutes for Research*
- Understanding the Costs of Implementing Illinois' Learning Renewal—Social Emotional Learning (LR-SEL) Initiatives in Schools. *Stephanie Levin, American Institutes for Research; Christopher Brooks, American Institutes for Research; Katherine Laird, American Institutes for Research*
- Widening Tuition Gaps: Financial Disparities Among U.S. Public Universities. *Jungwook Kim, University of Cincinnati; Seonjin Kim, Miami University (OH); Joel R. Malin, Miami University (OH)*

Chairs: *Mariano Lozano-Soto, San Diego State University; Lena Batt, University of Kansas*

75.057. Transforming through Lesson Study: Building Collaborative Communities for Equitable and Engaging Learning. SIG-Lesson Study; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Georgia II;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

- Understanding a Positive Outlier: How Lesson Study and Problem-solving Shape Students' Experiences in Learning Math. *Catherine C. Lewis, Mills College at Northeastern*

University; Diana Marcela Galvez Bohorquez, San Francisco Unified School District; Norma Ming, Socos Labs

Building a Community of Practice: Mathematics Education Faculty and Graduate Students' Collaboration through Lesson Study. *Hongze Zhu, University of Florida; Melissa M. Soto, University of Florida; Aimaral Tabarak, University of Florida; Kristen Apraiz, University of Florida; Sheida Moghtader Eslami, University of Florida; Ri Ayat Ainul Bashirah, University of Florida; Kayla Sutcliffe, University of Florida; Hong Zhang, University of Florida*

Teacher Learning during a Virtual, Multi-Site Lesson Study Project. *Jada Kohlmeier, Auburn University; Jesus Tirado, Auburn University; David T. Marshall, Auburn University; Matthew F. Summerlin, Auburn University; Megan Andrews, Auburn University; Steven P. Brown, Auburn University*

How Technology-Mediated Lesson Study Enhances Rural Science Teachers' Capacity to Teach Three-Dimensional Science. *Michelle Hudson, Brigham Young University; Heather Leary, Brigham Young University; Rebecca Sansom, Texas A&M University; Max L. Longhurst, Utah State University; Clara Smith, Brigham Young University; Josh Stowers, Brigham Young University; Austin Moore, Utah State University*

Chair: *Rongjin Huang, Middle Tennessee State University*
Discussant: *Jennifer M. Suh, George Mason University*

75.058. Measuring What Matters: Challenges and Opportunities in Assessing Critical Thinking. SIG-Measurement and Assessment in Higher Education; Paper Session
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 6th Floor, Broadway; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Measuring the Efficacy of a Critical-Thinking Skills Program. *Doris Zahner, Council for Aid to Education; Michael Alexander, Texas A&M University; Lisa Provines, Texas A&M University*

Critical Thinking Performance Patterns among Australian and Chinese Higher Education Students: A Latent Profile Analysis. *Sundance Zhihong Sun, University of Melbourne*

Development and Validation of the 21st Century Skills Self-Efficacy Scale. *Laura Thomsen Morello, University of Bridgeport; John Chick, University of Bridgeport*

Exploring Key Features for Effective Machine Learning Scoring of Science Constructed Responses. *Heqiao Wang, Old Dominion University; Kevin Haudek, Michigan State University; Amanda Manzanares, Denver Museum of Nature & Science; Caterina B. Azzarello, University of Northern Colorado; Chelsie Romulo, University of Northern Colorado*

Refining the Core Competency Scale for University Students: A Graded Response Model Approach. *Yewon Kim, Ewha Womans University; Junseo Kim, Korea University; John Jongho Park, Pennsylvania State University; Mihee Park, Auburn University*

Chair: *Patrick Obot, University of Houston*
Discussant: *Marjorie L. Dorime-Williams, MDRC*

75.059. Equity, Technology, and Emerging Literacies. SIG-Multicultural/Multiethnic Education: Theory, Research and Practice; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum G; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Culturally Responsive AI Adoption in Teacher Education: Insights from Multicultural Educators. *Nayif Adil Awad, Sakhnin College; Shira Soffer-Vital, Ono Academic College*

Exclusions: Using AI to Uplift Minority Voices in STEM Higher Education. *Show Mei Lin, Tennessee State University*

Exploring Racial Disparities in Digital Reading: A QuantCrit Study of U.S. Adolescents. *Ibrahim Kizil, Syracuse University; Bong Gee Jang, Syracuse University*

Chair: *Samira Said Al Hosni, Indiana University*
Discussant: *Matthew Nyaaba, University of Georgia*

75.060. Rasch Model Applications including AI. SIG-Rasch Measurement; Paper Session
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 6th Floor, Mission; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Comparing Rating Quality between GenAI and Human Raters for ELL Writing Assessment: An MFRM Analysis. *Wei Huang, University of Alabama; Jujia Li, University of Alabama*

Exploring Human, Empirical, and AI-Derived Item Classifications to Predict Item Difficulty in Educational Assessments. *Jing Li, University of Georgia; Cheng Tang, University of Georgia; Chan Lu, University of Georgia; Matthew J. Madison, University of Georgia; George Engelhard, University of Georgia*

Judging the Judges: A Rasch Analysis of Human and Large Language Model Raters. *Cheng Tang, University of Georgia; Jing Li, University of Georgia; Jiawei Xiong, Curriculum Associates; George Engelhard, University of Georgia*

Measuring preservice teachers' beliefs about grading-as-feedback: Examining novice understandings in preservice settings. *Carrie Holmberg, San José State University; Brent Duckor, San José State University*

Modeling Rater Judgments on AI-Aided Rubrics: A Rasch-Based Mixed Methods Study. *Beyza Aksu-Dunya, Bartin University; Talip Gülle, Jyväskylä University; Mehmet Can Demir*

75.061. Diasporic Sankofān desires: Looking back to Africa to unforget Black histories and (re)imagine Black futures. SIG-Research Focus on Black Education; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 403B; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

- Looking Back & Fetching: Unforgetting African Present(s) & Forging Black Futures. *Kgosietsile Velempini, University of North Carolina Wilmington; Romeo Abraham, University of North Carolina - Wilmington*
- Looking Back & Fetching: Diasporan Perspectives & Impacts. *Crystal G Simmons, University of North Carolina - Wilmington; Michele A. Parker, University of North Carolina - Wilmington*
- Looking Back & Fetching: Unforgetting histories & birthing futures with quilting performances. *Julia Lynch, University of North Carolina - Wilmington; Candace M. Thompson, University of North Carolina - Wilmington*
- Chair: *Shawn S. Savage, University of North Carolina - Wilmington*
- Discussant: *Shawn S. Savage, University of North Carolina - Wilmington*

75.062. Rhythms of Resistance: Black Aesthetics, Sensorial Literacies, and the Architecture of Educational Liberation. SIG-Research Focus on Black Education; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 506;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

- Bands Can Make Them Dance: A Neurological Lens on the Impact of Urban High School Band Programs on Black Students. *Kevin L. Jones, Stephen F. Austin State University*
- Liberation through Literacy: A Critical Ethnography of Black Youth Poetics Through Hip-Hop Based Education. *Imani J. Wallace, University of Massachusetts - Amherst*
- Restorying Black Place Relations through Afrofuturist Art. *Maya Revell, University of Oregon*
- Exploring the Radical Love Pedagogies of Black Women Early Childhood Educators Through Endarkened Poetic Inquiry. *Meghan L. Green, Erikson Institute*
- (Earth)Seeds of Liberation: Using Parable Praxis to Dream of New Worlds with Black Girls. *Alexis Morgan Young, Michigan State University*
- Chair: *Asif Wilson, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*
- Discussants: *Shelton K. Johnson, SUNY New Paltz; Neisha Terry Young, Stony Brook University - SUNY*

75.063. Leveraging Research-Practice Partnerships to Develop Open-Access and Scalable Reading Assessments: Rapid Online Assessment of Reading. SIG-Research in Reading and Literacy; Symposium
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Beaudry A; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

- Bridging the Lab and Classroom: Innovations in Dyslexia Screening through a Research-Practice Partnership Model. *Jason D Yeatman, Stanford University*
- Improving A Single-Word Recognition Assessment:

- Adaptivity, Engagement, and Floor Effects. *Wanjing Ma, Stanford University; Mia Fuentes-Jimenez, Stanford University; Jasmine Tran, University of California - Irvine; Carrie Townley Flores, Stanford University; Adam Richie-Halford, Stanford University; Benjamin Dominigue, Stanford University; Jason D Yeatman, Stanford University*
- Validation of ROAR Assessments: Made Possible through Research Practice Partnership. *Carrie Townley Flores, Stanford University; Mia Fuentes-Jimenez, Stanford University; Kelly Rose Wentzlof, Stanford University; Jason D Yeatman, Stanford University*
- Development of ROAR-Español: Created, Validated, and Normed for Spanish-Speaking Multilingual Learners. *Mia Fuentes-Jimenez, Stanford University; Kelly Rose Wentzlof, Stanford University; Wanjing Ma, Stanford University; Julian M. Siebert, University of California - San Francisco; Ana Saavedra, Stanford University; Carrie Townley Flores, Stanford University; Adam Richie-Halford, Stanford University; Jason D Yeatman, Stanford University*
- Screening Secondary Students for Reading Difficulties with the ROAR Comprehension Suite. *Tonya Murray, Stanford University; Youngsun Moon, Stanford University; Jason D Yeatman, Stanford University; Rebecca Silverman, Stanford University; Yukie Tomaya, University of California - Berkeley; Alexander Mario Blum, Stanford University; Robin Irey, University of California - San Francisco; Kelly Rose Wentzlof, Stanford University*
- Chair: *Youngsun Moon, Stanford University*
- Discussant: *Elfrieda H. Hiebert, TextProject*

75.064. Roles of School Climate, Identity, and Support in Response to Teacher-Targeted Violence: A Global Perspective. SIG-School Community, Climate, and Culture; Symposium
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Los Feliz; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

- "No Longer Have a Sense of Mission:" Teacher Victimization and Identity Reconstruction in South Korea. *Danbi Choe, Louisiana State University*
- Revisiting the Healthy Context Paradox: Teacher Victimization, Burnout, and School Climate in the U.S. *Jin Hyung Lim, University of California - Berkeley; Chunyan Yang, University of Maryland; Ella Rho, University of Maryland; Quennie Dong, University of California - Berkeley; Krandhasi Kodaiarasu, University of Maryland*
- Enhancing School Climate Through Collective Efficacy: Moderating Role of Teacher Victimization in Greek Schools. *Chryse (Sissy) Hatzichristou, National & Kapodistrian, University of Athens, Greece; Aikaterini Lampropoulou, National & Kapodistrian, University of Athens*
- Mapping Teacher Victimization and Support Networks: Cross-Country Comparison of China, Morocco, Türkiye, and U.S. *Chunyan Yang, University of Maryland; Ella Rho,*

University of Maryland; Chun Chen, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Adil Bentahar, University of Delaware; Ozge Hacifazlioglu, University of California - Berkeley; BILGE KALKAVAN, Hasan Kalyoncu University; Sinan Hopcan; Elif Polat, Istanbul University - Cerrahpasa

Chair: *Chunyan Yang, University of Maryland*

Discussant: *Linda Reddy, Rutgers University*

75.065. Discourse, Semiosis, and Justice from Early Childhood to Adolescence. SIG-Semiotics in Education: Signs, Meanings and Multimodality; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 501C;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Deconstructing Exclusion: An Appraisal Analysis of Arguments Justifying Preschool Suspension and Expulsion. *Erin E. Flynn, University of Michigan; Yiğit Savuran, University of Michigan; Dalia Avello Vega, University of Edinburgh; Qingqing Yan, University of Michigan; Rayna Emilova, University of Michigan*

Exploring Semiotic Conflicts in Integrated Math-CS Lessons with Coding Toys. *Jessica Lajos, Utah State University; Asmaa Yazidi Alaoui, Utah State University; Jody E. Clarke-Midura, Utah State University; Anahita Ashineh, Utah State University; Deborah Silvis, SUNY - College at Cortland; Camille Lund, Utah State University; Jessica F. Shumway, Utah State University; Boram Lee, Utah State University*

Meaning in the Making: Revealing the Convergence of Languaging, Semiosis, Knowledge, and Culture in Digital Video Composing. *Qianqian Ma, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Chunhong Liu, Simon Fraser University*

Speaking Care, Community, and Cultural Responsiveness into Being: Leveraging Instructional Conversations to Develop Thriving Learners. *Melissa Ann Holmes, Kansas State University*

Chair: *Judith L. Green, University of California - Santa Barbara*

75.066. Reimagining Inclusion and Equity in Early Childhood Education. SIG-Special and Inclusive Education Research; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum J;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Toward Inclusive Flourishing: Centering Culture and Disability in Early Childhood Education. *Youme Kim, University of Kansas; Gregory Cheatham, University of Kansas*

A Framework for Inclusion: Values Behind 50 Years of Practice. *Cam Michael Powell, Syracuse University; Sara H. Petit-McClure, Syracuse University; Teukie Martin, Syracuse University; Christine Elaine Ashby, Syracuse University*

Systematic Disparities in Early Childhood Disability Services: Provider Training and Service Gaps. *Priyanshi Sharma, Stanford University; Melissa Mares, Stanford University;*

Sihong Liu, Stanford University; Phil Fisher, Stanford University

Transitions That Work for Whom? Reimagining Equity in Early Childhood Special Education. *Ruby Batz, University of Nevada - Reno; Maiko Hata, University of Oregon; Lauren Cycyk, University of Oregon; Gauri Bharadwaj, University of Oregon; Ben Sanders, Oregon Health and Science University; Katherine E. Zuckerman, Oregon Health and Science University*

Chair: *Xinxia Li, The George Washington University*

75.067. Promoting Trauma-Informed Education and Youth Well-Being. SIG-Stress, Coping, and Resilience; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304B;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Heart and Soul of Equitable, Ambitious Teaching: You“brought evidence... you also brought yourself”. *Addison Duane, Sacramento State University; Simona Goldin, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Debi Khasnabis, University of Michigan; Alex Shevrin Venet, Community College of Vermont*

Nurturing Hope: How Educators Can Understand and Support Teens After a Wildfire. *Lindsey Nenadal, California State University - Chico; Grace Borgeson, California State University - Chico; Maricella Garcia, California State University - Chico; Madeline Mauldwin, California State University - Chico; Lizbeth Navarro, California State University - Chico; Karen Parmar, California State University - Chico; Guadalupe Carolina Vazquez, California State University - Chico*

Synthesizing Practice-Based Evidence from Trauma Research: A Dual-Case Study of Review Impact and Epistemic Transformation. *Adam J. Alvarez, Texas A&M University; M. Shelley Thomas, University of Louisville; Shantel Crosby, University of Louisville*

Unaccompanied but Not Unsupported: Central American-origin Adolescents' Experiences of Schooling and Coping in the U.S. *Jessica Trejos, City University of New York*

Chair: *Addison Duane, Sacramento State University*

Discussant: *Adam J. Alvarez, Texas A&M University*

75.068. Honoring the Legacy of Dr. Barry J. Zimmerman, a Co-Sponsored AERA Session from Division C, Motivation Special Interest Group, and Studying and Self-Regulated Learning Special Interest Group. SIG-Studying and Self-Regulated Learning Cosponsored with Division C - Learning and Instruction, SIG-Motivation in Education; Invited Roundtable
Westin Bonaventure, Level 3, Hollywood Ballroom;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Theme 1: Self-Regulated Learning and Advanced Learning

- Technologies (Table 1 Chair). *Roger Azevedo, University of Central Florida*
- Theme 1: Self-Regulated Learning in the Age of AI: Rethinking Graduate Professional Development (Table 1). *Hilal Ayan, Florida State University*
- Theme 1: Motivation Science Meets Teacher Education: A Mixed-Methods Study of a Chatbot-Supported Workshop to Enhance Pre-Service Teachers' Motivational Competencies (Table 1). *Wonjoon Cha, The Ohio State University*
- Theme 1: Leveling Up Motivation in Research: A Mixed Methods Study on a Digital Game-based Learning Workshop (Table 1). *Megan Marguerite Hokama, University of Arizona*
- Theme 1: Designing AI-Enhanced Learning Experiences for Self-Regulated Learning (Table 1). *Qiyang Lin, Michigan State University*
- Theme 1: AI-Powered Digital Literacy as a Pathway to Self-Regulated Learning (Table 1). *Salih Mansur, Touro University*
- Theme 2: The Development of Self-Regulated Learning Across Domains (Table 2 Chair). *Anastasia Kitsantas, George Mason University*
- Theme 2: The Role of Music in Self-Regulated Studying (Table 2). *Bridget K. Daleiden, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*
- Theme 2: GenAI Use and Self-Regulated Learning in Undergraduate Engineering Students (Table 2). *Jennie Lee, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*
- Theme 2: Undergraduate Students' Emotions and Sense of Belonging in STEM (Table 2). *Maham Khalid, University of Arizona*
- Theme 2: Teacher Support Predicts Curiosity, Self-Regulated Learning, and Belonging: Evidence from PISA 2022 (Indonesia) (Table 2). *Asis Wahyudi, Pennsylvania State University*
- Theme 3: Self-Regulated Learning Assessment and Intervention (Table 3 Chair). *Timothy J. Cleary, Rutgers University*
- Theme 3: From Support to Self-Direction: Linking Need-Supportive Teaching, Resilience, and Self-Regulated Learning (Table 3). *Beth A. Hosek, George Mason University*
- Theme 3: Beyond the Red Pen: How Students Make Sense of Feedback (Table 3). *Alicia Jane Peras, University of Arizona*
- Theme 3: Navigating the Shift to Personalized, Competency-Based Learning: Understanding the Lived Experiences of Educators (Table 3). *Alyson Wright, University of Georgia*
- Theme 3: A Comparative Review of Learning Motivation Scales for English Learners (Table 3). *Yan Wu, Johns Hopkins University*
- Theme 4: Barry J. Zimmerman: A Trailblazer of Social and Cultural Self-Regulated Learning (Table 4 Chair). *Hefer Bembenuitty, Queens College - CUNY*
- Theme 4: Cognitive Load, Overload, and Self-Regulation: A Phenomenological Study of Neurodivergent College Students (Table 4). *Amanda Elizabeth Evans, University of Central Florida*
- Theme 4: Media and STEM Motivation: Gender and Racial Differences on Media Influence and STEM Motivation (Table 4). *Kitley Ann Kern, University of Cincinnati*
- Theme 4: Bridging Theory and Practice – Intersections between Culturally Responsive Teaching and Situated Expectancy Value Theory (Table 4). *Caleb Wang Yuan, University of Arizona*
- Theme 4: Executive Functioning and Self Regulation: What Is The Difference For Students With ADHD? (Table 4). *John P Burrell, University of Connecticut*
- Theme 5: Self-Regulation and Academic Learning (Table 5 Chair). *Steve Graham, Arizona State University*
- Theme 5: Online Self-Regulated Learning among Undergraduates: A Latent Profile Analysis (Table 5). *Eric Asare, Old Dominion University*
- Theme 5: Examining Prior Knowledge, Expectancy-Value Beliefs, and Achievement-related Choices and Outcomes in Undergraduate Biology (Table 5). *Michael Abdul Ghani Berro, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*
- Theme 5: Managing Time and Studying with Peers: Predicting the Use of Retrieval Practice and Spacing (Table 5). *Serena Luo, The Ohio State University; Soo-Hong Yim, The Ohio State University*
- Theme 5: What Drives and Drains Student STEM Engagement and Achievement? The Role of Situated Expectancy-Value Profiles (Table 5). *Qingqing Zhou, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*
- Theme 6: Monitoring Accuracy, Calibration, and Confidence (Table 6 Chair). *Linda Bol, Old Dominion University*
- Theme 6: Reading Between the Modes: Enhancing Undergraduate Multimodal Comprehension Through Training Videos (Table 6). *Jannah Fusenig, University of Maryland*
- Theme 6: Teachers as Co-regulators: Scaffolding Student Uncertainty Navigation in Science Learning (Table 6). *Yu Ye, Arizona State University*
- Theme 6: Gesturing Uncertainty in Introductory Physics Collaborative Learning (Table 6). *Minghui Zhu, University at Buffalo - SUNY*
- Theme 6: Regulatory Focus and the Testing Effect: Cognitive and Motivational Pathways of Retrieval Practice (Table 6). *Vishal Easwar, Boston College*
- Theme 7: Developing Self-Regulated Learners to Meet the Demands of Reading and Writing in the Elementary Grades (Table 7 Chair). *Karen R. Harris, Independent Consultant*
- Theme 7: Examining Teachers' Perspectives on Khanmigo: A Case Study of AI Implementation in K–12 Education (Table 7). *Kolawole Michael Afolabi, Oklahoma State University*
- Theme 7: Exploring Self-Regulated Learning Strategies in AI-Supported EFL Writing (Table 7). *Azzah Alzahrani, University at Buffalo - SUNY*
- Theme 7: Predicting Preschoolers' Reading Engagement: The Roles of Self-Regulation and Early Literacy Skills (Table 7). *Alicia Delgado, University of Utah*

Theme 7: Every Voice Matters: Piloting an Equitable Classroom Discussion Protocol to Motivate All in Elementary Science (Table 7). *Lin Yan, Arizona State University*

Chairs: *Jason A. Chen, College of William & Mary; Helenrose Fives, Montclair State University; Michelle Taub, University of Central Florida*

75.069. Survey Science in Education: Methods, Analysis, and Emerging Technologies. SIG-Survey Research in Education; Paper Session
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Echo Park; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Analysis of Likert-type Items: Course Evaluations. *John D. Morris, Florida Atlantic University; Mary G. Lieberman, Florida Atlantic University; Maria D. Vásquez-Colina, Florida Atlantic University*

Reassessing Weights in Survey Research in Education: Implications for Multilevel Modeling. *Umut Atasever, IEA Hamburg; Francis H. Lim Huang, University of Missouri; Leslie Rutkowski, Indiana University*

Timing Is Everything—Or Is It? Comparing Survey Methods Used for Measuring Teachers' Perceived Growth. *Timothy D. Folger, Binghamton University - SUNY; Yiyun Fan, Binghamton University - SUNY; Casey E Hanna, Binghamton University - SUNY; Toni A. May, Binghamton University - SUNY*

Using Artificial Intelligence (AI) To Generate a Survey: A Step-by-Step Guide. *Ruiqin Gao, University of South Carolina; Christine DiStefano, University of South Carolina; Xiaobo Wei, University of South Carolina; Fang Wang, University of South Carolina*

Chair: *Jennifer Richardson McGee, Appalachian State University*

75.070. Negotiating Power and Translating Technology Policies and Standards into Practice. SIG-Technology as an Agent of Change in Teaching and Learning; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 2; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

"Make Sense, Not Sensors": A Case Study of Teacher Professional Sensemaking about AI Surveillance in Education. *Xingyuan Gao, East China Normal University*

From Mandate to Meaning: School Leadership and the Diffusion of Computational Thinking Standards. *Steven Azeka, Teachers College, Columbia University; Ellen B. Meier, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Confronting Algorithmic Bias: Equity-Centered Leadership Responses to Generative AI in Higher Education. *Pinyi Wang, University of Florida*

Chair: *Jiaju Lin, Pennsylvania State University*

Discussant: *Vanessa Hammler Kenon, University of Texas - San*

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Division and SIG Roundtables

75.071. AERA Roundtable Session Saturday 11:45 am;
Roundtable Session

75.071-1. Responding to Polycrises: Educational Leadership Across Intersecting Challenges and Contexts (Table 1).

Division A - Administration; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Building Community Resilience and School Readiness Post-COVID. *Daniel J. Boudah, East Carolina University; Michael Sasscer*

Counting the Cost: How I.C.E. Raids Complicate School Budgets and Planning. *Megan K. Rauch Griffard, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Mark Spinrad, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Bradley Marianno, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*

The Diverse Roles of Schools in Climate Change Adaptation: A Global Perspective. *Kaylee Allison Laub, University of California - Santa Barbara; Danielle B. Harlow, University of California - Santa Barbara; Simone Pulver, University of California - Santa Barbara; Sarah Anderson, University of California - Santa Barbara*

Worldmindedness or America First? Leading through Curriculum Controversy in the Los Angeles Schools, 1948-1953. *Lauri Johnson, Boston College*

Chair: *Charles L. Lowery, Virginia Tech*

75.071-2. Curriculum Across Contexts: Philosophies, Policies, and Indigenous Futures (Table 2).

Division B - Curriculum Studies; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Historicizing Equity and Excellence in High School Curriculum Policy Discourse in South Korea. *Ji-Hye Kim, Korean Educational Development Institute*

"I don't know the Treaty of Fort Pitt": Civics, Treaties and Curriculum. *Rachel Talbert, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Temporal and Spatial Conceptions of Bildung: A Systematic Research Review 1990-2020. *Armend Tahirsylaj, Norwegian University of Science and Technology; Marit Honerod Hoveid, Norwegian University of Science and Technology*

The Practical Tradition in China's Basic Education Curriculum: Past Progress and Future Prospects. *Helen Gao, East China Normal University*

Chair: *Shaoru Liang, Shangping Middle School*

75.071-3. The Battle for Higher Education and Historical Truth(s) (Table 3). Division F - Historical Inquiry in Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

From Correspondence to Zoom: A Historical Review of Distance Learning and Its Persistent Challenges. *Isabela Thebaldi, University of Florida; Lindsay Byron, University of Florida*

Loyola Marymount and the Long Arc of Jesuit Continuing Education. *Mark E. Houlemarde, Loyola Marymount University*

Preserving Historical Truth in an Era of Postmodern Academic Reconstruction. *Lindsay Byron, University of Florida; Isabela Thebaldi, University of Florida*

Student Protest, Crisis Response, and National Narratives: Using Historical Perspective to Interpret the Present. *Allison Palmadessa, Greensboro College; Erica Eckert, Kent State University; Mary Kate Steinbeck, University of Georgia*

Chair: *Kyle J. Williams, The Ohio State University*

75.071-4. Exploring Diversity in Play in Children's Storytelling (Table 4). Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

“‘All Messi’s Ballon d’Ors Were Rigged’: How Children’s Soccer Passion Develops Critical Literacy at Home”. *Jubara AbuSin, Pennsylvania State University*

Collective Magic for Regenerating & Repairing Education: Black and Chicana Feminist Multimodal Story Sharing Playgrounds. *Paty Abril-Gonzalez, University of Texas at Austin; Zachary Rupp, University of Texas - Austin; Tia C. Madkins, The University of Texas at Austin; Ofelia Castro Schepers, Purdue University*

Kaambal: Children’s Multimodal Perceptions of Learning in Rural Public Schools in Yucatán. *Adriana Alvarez, University of Colorado - Denver; Daniela Brito Calderón, Instituto Tecnológico y de Estudios Superiores de Monterrey; Dafne Vergara Lozada, Centro de Investigación y Docencia Económicas; Paula Cortina Bonnin, Instituto Tecnológico Autónomo de México; María Elena Ortega Hesles, Independent Researcher*

Narratives of Resistance: International Holocaust Children’s Literature as a Site for Peace Literacy. *Jan Lacina, Texas Christian University*

Undergraduates’ Critical Media Analysis of Picturebooks about Immigration. *Audrey Lucero, University of Oregon*

Chair: *Yetunde S. Alabede, Michigan State University*

75.071-5. International and Post-Colonial Contexts for Social

Justice Leadership (Table 5). SIG-Leadership for Social Justice; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Listening as Leadership: Centering Quiet Virtue and Youth Agency in China. *Xiaohang Luo, University of Pennsylvania; Yuting Wang, Beijing Normal University*

On the Institutional Edge: Crafting New Leadership for Educational Change in India. *Madhu Narayanan, Florida International University*

Notes from the Front Porch: Social Justice Leadership in the South. *Brandi N. Hinnant-Crawford, Clemson University; Jacquelyn Williams, Clemson University*

Systems Justice and Decolonial “Self”-Actualization: Cultivated Storytelling of Principal Turnover Intentions in Marginalized School Communities. *Kathryn Lige, San Francisco State University*

Accepting the Challenge: The Liminality of Equity Directors Building Capacity in K-12 School Districts. *Kristin Shawn Huggins, Washington State University; Leslie Ann Locke, Minnesota State University - Mankato; Regina Lynn Seabrook, University of Minnesota; Emily Colton, University of Minnesota; Darrius A. Stanley, University of Minnesota*

Chair: *Anna Louise Baird, California State University - Dominguez Hills*

75.071-6. Troubled Organizational Waters: Racial Equity/Inequity, Politics, and Change (Table 6). SIG-Organizational Theory; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Stuck in the Middle: How Organizational Change Affects Middle-status Employee Groups in an Academic Library. *Jennifer Lauren Nelson, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Making Sense of Racial Equity: Staff Perspectives in Creative Learning Organizations. *Ashlyn Salvage, University of Pittsburgh*

Stay in Your Lane, Speak with One Voice: How School Board Norms Perpetuate Racial Inequity. *Ann LoBue, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Crossing Partisan Lines: Social-Emotional Learning Diffusion Across U.S. States in an Era of Polarization. *Tom Nachtigal, Stanford University*

Conscientization Amid Sensemaking Cycles: A Theoretical Framework for Researching Educational Change in Divisive Times. *Gregory Vincent Massara, University at Albany - SUNY*

Chair: *Susan Bush-Mecenas, RAND Corporation*

75.071-7. SIG 17: Complexity Theories in Education Round Table Session (Table 7). SIG-Complexity Theories in

Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Addressing Inequitable Learning Gaps Using Agent-based Modeling and the ICAP Framework. *Zayaan Khan, University of California - Irvine; Shayan Doroudi, University of California - Irvine*

Domain Structure and Complexity in the Cognitive Theory of Multimedia Learning: A Systematized Review. *Elvin José Fortuna, Michigan State University; Tingting Li, Washington State University*

The Queer Joy Toolbox: An Ecological Approach to Understanding Queer Joy Among K-12 Teachers. *Travis Jon Dean, University of Arizona*

Chair: *Jonathan C. Hilpert, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*
Discussant: *Emma P. Bullock, Sam Houston State University*

75.071-8. Transnational Philosophy, Democratic Practice, and Moral Education: Conceptual Perspectives on Dewey (Table 8). SIG-Dewey Studies; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Calling Without a Caller: Dewey, Hansen, and the Master Butcher. *Daoyong Ding, Beijing Normal University*

John Dewey: From Industrialization to the Viral Era. *Todd Alan Price, National Louis University; Rose M. Ylimaki, Northern Arizona University*

Reclaiming Norms Through Moral Education: Deweyan Perspectives. *Roudy Hildreth, University of Colorado - Boulder*

The Reception and Transformation of John Dewey's Thought in Modern China: Focusing on Hu Shih and Tao Xingzhi. *James Yang, Beijing Normal-Hong Kong Baptist University*

Chair: *Austin J. Pickup, Aurora University*

75.071-9. Community-Rooted Approaches and AANHPI Communities (Table 9). SIG-Asian Americans and Pacific Islanders in Education and Research; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

A Photovoice Study on Language and Culture Preservation in Vietnamese Dual Language Immersion. *Evelyn Nha Khanh Nguyen, California State University - Long Beach*

Archipelagic Thinking in Teacher Education: Mapping transnational relations between Asian American and Filipino teacher candidates. *Camille Ungco, University of Washington*

Centering Pakikipagkwentuhan as Method: Filipino American School Leaders and the Power of Story. *John Edward Estoesta, Claremont Graduate University*

Talanoa as a Research Method(ology): Exploring its Utility and

Application in Higher Education Research. *Demeturie Toso-Lafaele Gogue, University of Massachusetts - Boston; Natasha A. Saelua, Texas State University*

Chair: *Xiu Cravens, Vanderbilt University*

75.071-10. Data, Policy, and Access: Participation and Pathways with AANHPI Communities (Table 10). SIG-Asian Americans and Pacific Islanders in Education and Research; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Campus Resource Use Among Asian American Native Hawaiian Pacific Islander First-Generation and Continuing Generation Students. *Annie Bae, University of California - Los Angeles*

Graduate School Choice among Native Hawaiian and Pacific Islander Students: A Critical Race Theory Approach. *Marlena Wolfgramm, Council of Graduate Schools; Eligio Martinez, Cal Poly Pomona; Dina C. Maramba, Claremont Graduate University*

Untangling Asian American Political Participation: Education, Immigrant Status, Political Generation, and Political Trust. *Yun Rachel Liang, Touro University*

Chair: *Eujin Park, Stanford University*

75.072. AERA Roundtable Session Saturday 11:45 am - Gold 1; Roundtable Session

75.072-1. Roundtable Session 6: Student Learning and Development in College and Beyond (Table 1). Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Does Experience Influence Experience? Understanding Student Perceptions of Problem-Based Learning Through Teaching Evaluations. *Shirong Zhang, Maastricht University; Laurie Delnoij, Maastricht University; Wim H. Gijssels, Maastricht University; Inken Gast, Maastricht University*

Effects of Remote Academic Advising through Synchronous Communication Technology. *Xiaoxue Wang, Florida Gulf Coast University; Yanqiong Liu, Florida Gulf Coast University; Michael Houdyshell, Florida Gulf Coast University*

Exploring Self-Doubt in Community College Computer Science: Evidence from Exploratory Factor Analysis. *Trenton Dawson, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*

Prevalence and Determinants of Cyberloafing among College of Education Students in Ghana. *Francis Nyamekye, Kibi College of Education; Ivy Nkrumah, University of Cape Coast; Regina Nugba, University of Cape Coast; Ebenezer Takyi-Wadieh, Ohio University; Ama Boatemah Sarpong, Kibi College of Education*

What are Two-Stage Tests Good for? A Synthesis of the Literature. *Stephen Politzer-Ahles, University of Kansas; Min Liang, The Education University of Hong Kong*

75.072-2. Discipline/Police/Incarceration (Table 2). Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

College-Going Aspirations and Behaviors Among Adolescent Boys Who Have Been School Disciplined and School Policed. *Collin Perryman, Arizona State University; Spencer Platt, University of South Carolina*

Explaining the Transitional Experiences and Persistence of Formerly Incarcerated Students in Four-Year Institutions: A Grounded Theory Analysis. *Jude Paul Matias Dizon, California State University - East Bay*

The role of information and expectations on the development of a higher education student identity. *Paula Clasing-Manquian, PUC; Maria Veronica Santelices, Catholic University of Chile*

Chair: *Dashana Lane, Bethune Cookman University*

75.072-3. Global learning and advancing student success (Table 3). Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

A Study on the Mechanisms Influencing Academic Integration Among Master's Students. *Qintao SUN, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Yueqi SHI, Nanjing University*
"I don't deserve here": a case study on Hong Kong first-generation undergraduates' well-being. *Clive Ka-lun Lee, The University of Hong Kong*

Transnational Academia in Flux: The Hong Kong PhD in the Global Academic Labor Market. *Ewan Wright, The Education University of Hong Kong; Artem Zadorozhnyy, The Education University of Hong Kong*

Chair: *Jie Lin, Shanghai Jiao Tong University*

75.072-4. Equity-Based Scholarship on Academic Contexts and Careers (Table 4). Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Envisioning Kahiki: Teaching to Collectively (Re)Imagine Higher Education Futures. *Nicole Alia Salis Reyes, University of Hawai'i at Manoa; Rachel Haulani Loo, University of Hawai'i at Manoa*

Exploring Faculty Salary Inequities Between Minority-Serving and non Minority-Serving Institutions of Higher Education. *Zach Taylor, John Burton Advocates for Youth*

Graduate Preparation for Equity and Social Justice: Faculty and Student Perspectives from Higher Education/Student Affairs Programs. *Avery B. Olson, California State University - Long Beach; Cara Demyra Askew, California State University - Long Beach*

Reading the Tea Leaves: Faculty awareness of Latino/x collegiate men's help-seeking behavior. *Luis Ponjuan, Texas A&M University; Rodrigo Aguayo, University of Texas at Austin; Jase Kugiya, University of Texas at Austin; Victor B. Sáenz, University of Texas at Austin*

75.072-5. Place Based Innovations: A Regional Rocus on Education and Economic Development (Table 5). Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Degrees of Growth: A Quasi-Experimental Study of Community College Baccalaureate Effects on County-Level Economies. *Jin-Kwon LEE, Korean Educational Development Institute; Hannah Kim, Seoul National University; Jeong Youn Lee, Seoul National University; Bawool Hong, Korea University*

Higher Education Expansion and Regional Innovation: Evidence from China's Tech-Based SMEs. *Peining Mao, East China Normal University; Chen Xie, East China Normal University; Jiabin Fu, East China Normal University*

The Untapped Potential of Noncredit Education: Restructuring Pathways for Texas' Postsecondary and Workforce Goals. *Susana H. Hernandez, Northern Arizona University; Christopher Burnett, Houston Community College; Andrea Bakscheider Burrige, Houston Community College; Lyle McKinney, University of North Florida*

75.072-6. From Theory to Transformation: Preparing Justice-Oriented Educators Through Critical Literacy, Equity, and Practice (Table 6). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

A Reading Specialist Candidate's Enactment of Equity Pedagogy for Reluctant Writers During a Virtual Literacy Clinic, embedded in a Detroit Public School Community District and University Collaboration. *K. Dara Hill, University of Michigan - Dearborn*

Examining Asset-Based Pedagogical Development for Preservice Language Teachers: Theory into Practice. *Ziqi Li, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Timothy Monreal, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Erin Kearney, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

From Statistics to Social Critique: Prospective Teachers Engaging with Civic Data. *Ayşe Ozturk, Old Dominion*

University; Ozgul Kartal, University of Wisconsin - Whitewater

How conceptual fidelity and pair comparisons affect learning processes using video examples for planning knowledge.

Rieke Frerichs, Europa-Universität Flensburg; Tim Heemsoth, Europa-Universität Flensburg

Implementing Critical Visual Literacy in Teacher Education to Promote Culturally Responsive Teaching Practices for All Students. *Hyeju Han, National Louis University; Xiaoning Chen, National Louis University*

Chair: *Ziqi Li, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

75.072-7. Culturally Responsive Pathways in Preservice Teacher Education: Identity, Global Experiences, and Literature-Based Pedagogy (Table 7). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Humanizing Asynchronous Teacher Preparation: Developing Pre-service Teachers' Understanding of Intersectional Identity. *Kelly Lormand, Grand Valley State University; Katie F. Whitley, Montclair State University*

Literature, Identity, and Pedagogical Growth: Exploring Culturally Sustaining Pedagogy Through Cross-Cultural Book Clubs. *Steven Hart, California State University - Fresno; Susan V. Bennett, University of South Florida - St. Petersburg*

Pre-service Teacher Learning from Field Experiences During a Study Abroad Program. *Mark T. Enfield, Elon University; Jeffrey P. Carpenter, Elon University; Heidi Hollingsworth, Elon University; Bill Burress, Elon University*

Unforgetting to Imagine: A Pre-Service Teacher's Autoethnographic Journey Toward Culturally Responsive Futures. *Deneen S. Dixon-Payne, Towson University; Alyssa Geddie, Towson University; Marcia J. Watson-Vandiver, Towson University*

Urban Education Culturally-Based Internships in Teacher Education: A Review of the Literature. *Leanne M. Evans, University of Wisconsin - Milwaukee; Wanying Liang, University of Wisconsin - Milwaukee; Jennifer Khasawneh, University of Wisconsin - Milwaukee; Renee Lindsey, University of Wisconsin - Milwaukee; Jamie Utecht, University of Wisconsin - Milwaukee*

Chair: *Mark T. Enfield, Elon University*

75.072-8. Advancing In-Service Professional Development for Teacher Socio-emotional Competencies (Table 8). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Can resilience and teacher professional growth lead to school

success? A structural equation approach. *James Ko, The Education University of Hong Kong; Ye Wang, The Education University of Hong Kong; Haiyan Qian, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Allan David Walker, The Education University of Hong Kong*

How Can the Use of Virtual Reality in Professional Development Increase Teacher Empathy? *Joanna R. Smith, University of Auckland; Frauke Meyer, The University of Auckland; Christine Margaret Rubie-Davies, University of Auckland; Georgia Rudd, The University of Auckland; Hana O'Regan, Tawhiri Consulting; Pam O'Connell, CORE Education; Roseanna Baker, University of Auckland; Melina Amos, Auckland University*

How Perceived Social-Emotional Competence and Teacher Self-Efficacy Influence Teachers' Job Crafting. *Shiyu Zhang, University of Hong Kong; Xianhan Huang, The Education University of Hong Kong; Chan Wang, The Education University of Hong Kong; Wen SHAO, University of Hong Kong; Mingyao Sun, Hong Kong Polytechnic University*

How Teachers' Self-Efficacy and Self-Directed Learning Beliefs Shape Their Teaching Quality: A Network Analysis. *Xin Zhang, Zhejiang University of Finance & Economics*

Teacher Value Beliefs for Professional Learning: Development and Associations with Enjoyment, Effectiveness, and Engagement. *Nayssan Safavian, University of California - Irvine; Catherine Bitter, American Institutes for Research; Jingtong Pan, American Institutes for Research; Molly E. Cain, American Institutes for Research; Katherine Laird, American Institutes for Research; Deborah Rodriguez, American Institutes for Research; Ayele Shakur, Campus Without Walls*

Chair: *Aya M. Isaac, University at Albany - SUNY*

75.073. AERA Roundtable Session Saturday 11:45 am - Gold 2; Roundtable Session

75.073-1. Rooted and Resilient: Innovative Approaches to Teacher Recruitment, Preparation, and Mentoring (Table 1). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

An Asset-Based Approach to Building Equitable Systems that Retain Educators in Title I Schools. *Nicole Duran-White, Los Angeles Unified School District*

Beyond Vulnerability: Resilience of Novice Teachers in China's Educational Reform—A Qualitative Study of an AWaRE Model Analysis. *Wenxin Gao, East China Normal University*

"Grow Your Own" in Action: Cultivating Future Teachers Through Community-Driven Pathways in California's Central Valley. *Ana Robles York, California State University*

- Stanislaus

Strengthening the Teacher Pipeline: Combining Grow Your Own and Residency Models to Empower Paraprofessionals. *Katrina Duarte-Meng, University of Texas - El Paso; Erika L. Mein, University of Texas - El Paso; Angelica Monarrez, University of Texas - El Paso; Jennifer Stefania Herrera Lozano, University of Texas - El Paso*

We Were Taught Why We Matter?: Exploring an HBCU-Based Alternative Teacher Residency Program. *Larkin Page, Xavier University of Louisiana; Jimmy Caldwell, Xavier University of Louisiana*

Chair: *Tara Kirton, Hunter College - CUNY*

Discussant: *Melody May Yin Isabela, Claremont Graduate University*

75.073-2. Bridging Gaps, Building Identities: Early Childhood Teachers in Transition (Table 2). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Bridging the Gaps: A Kindergarten Teacher's Identity Amid Digital Pressures and Developmental Practice. *Terri L. Hubbard, Polk State College & University of South Florida; Jolyn Blank, University of South Florida*

Early Learning, Uneven Ground; Transitional Kindergarten and Pre-Kindergarten from the Teachers' Perspectives. *Cheralen Arroyo Valdez, University of California - Santa Cruz*

K-1 Teacher Experiences with Multilingual Learners in US Public Schools. *Maria José A. Dias, Ball State University*

Men in a Woman's World? Understanding Professional Identity and Learning Differences in ECE Teacher Preparation. *Endale Fantahun Tadesse; Chunhai Gao, Shenzhen University; Sabika Khalid, Zhejiang Normal University*

Chair: *Terri L. Hubbard, Polk State College & University of South Florida*

75.073-3. Caring for Teachers: Stress, Isolation, and Collective Well-Being (Table 3). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

At the Center of Care: Exploring Early Childhood Educators' Trauma-Informed Practices in a Post-Earthquake Context. *Fatma Merve Yozgatli, Indiana University; Ela Sumeyye Secim, The Ohio State University*

Contemplative Practices and Teacher Stress: A Narrative Study of Head Start Educators. *Candice McKinnon, California State University - Channel Islands*

Depathologizing First-Year Teachers' Negative Feelings Through Collectivity: A Case Study On Feeling Bad. *Sara Staley, University of Colorado - Boulder; Zander Nowell,*

University of Colorado - Boulder; Bethy Leonardi, University of Colorado - Boulder

Exploring the Multilayered Nature of Teacher Isolation: An Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis. *Selahattin Turan, Bursa Uludag University; Firdevs Ozturk, Bursa Uludag University; Gulsah Yavuz; Damla Zumbul, Bursa Uludag University*

Preservice Teachers' Positive Mental Health Literacy, Openness to Psychological Help-seeking, and Well-being. *Ma. Jenina N. Nalipay, The Education University of Hong Kong*

Chair: *Sara Staley, University of Colorado - Boulder*

75.073-4. Being Otherwise: Narratives of Resistance and Renewal (Table 4). SIG-Narrative Research; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

"Are You Really a Writer?": Writing, Identity, and Transformation in a Korean Women's Writing Group. *Minkyung Choi, Montclair State University*

Critical Everyday: A Narrative Inquiry into a Teacher's Daily Pedagogies. *Heather J. Pinedo-Burns; Dana Frantz Bentley, Buckingham Browne and Nichols School*

Three Disabled Queers Enter an R1: One Strange Story Leaves. *Leia K. Cain, University of Tennessee; Anna Teitt, University of Tennessee; Leah Oakes, University of Tennessee*

"Open the Door and Then They Will Blossom": Translanguaging, Emotion Labor, and Emotional Capital. *Min Wang, SUNY New Paltz; Kerri McFadden, 216 Ryan School*

Chair: *Katrina Struloeff, University of Pennsylvania*

75.073-5. A Symposium of Innovative Attempts Toward Incremental Change for Mathematics Teachers (Table 5). SIG-Research in Mathematics Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Mathematics Coaching that Supports Incremental Improvements Toward More Equitable Mathematics Teaching. *Erica Litke, University of Delaware; Jonee Wilson, University of Virginia*

Incremental Professional Development for Fostering Small-Group Discourse. *Sarah Quebec Fuentes, Texas Christian University*

Incremental Change through a School-University Collaboration on Number Talks. *Temple A. Walkowiak, North Carolina State University; Heather West Jerez, Amplify Education, Inc.; Briana Pelton, Oberlin Magnet Middle School Wake County Public School; Kristin Hord, North Carolina State*

University

Interweaving Instructional Design and Professional Development to Advance Teachers' Aspirations to Improve Their Mathematics Teaching. *José Luis Cortina, Universidad Pedagógica Nacional; Jana Visnovska, The University of Queensland*

Examining the Varieties of Implementation within Nudge-Based Incremental Professional Development for Secondary Mathematics Teachers. *Samuel Otten, University of Missouri; Zandra de Araujo, University of Florida; Amber Grace Candela, University of Missouri - St. Louis*

Chair: *Samuel Otten, University of Missouri*

Discussant: *Jon R. Star, Harvard University*

75.073-6. Continuing the Explication of the Roles of Race and Culture in Mathematics Teaching and Learning (Table 6). SIG-Research in Mathematics Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Enacting Culturally Relevant Pedagogy: Insights from Black Women Mathematics Faculty. *Reagin Taylor McNeill, Michigan State University; Brittany L. Marshall, San Diego State University*

Mathematics Ability as Property: Examining Mathematics Reform as a Racial Project Through Raciolinguistic Genealogy. *Dan Battey, Rutgers University; Tasha Austin, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

Mathematics Teacher's Five-Year Journey with Culturally Relevant Pedagogy: Before, During and After a Professional Development. *Casedy A. Thomas, Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University; Robert Q. Berry, Indiana University*

Mathematics Teaching Practices of Culturally Relevant, Responsive, and Sustaining Pedagogy: A Qualitative Metasynthesis. *Jermaine R. Howell, Michigan State University*

Predictions of High School Math Achievement from HSLS: Mathematics Identity, Mathematics Self-Efficacy, and Racialized Identity. *Alexis Daniels, Johns Hopkins University*

Chair: *Nathan Alexander, Howard University*

75.073-7. Unpacking the Teaching and Learning of Middle School Mathematics (Table 7). SIG-Research in Mathematics Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

High-Dosage Tutoring Program for Middle School Mathematics. *Yan Wei, Southern Connecticut State University; Casey McPherson, Southern Connecticut State University; Alexandra J. Lamb, University of Connecticut;*

Eric J. Brunner, University of Connecticut; Stephen L. Ross, University of Connecticut

Impacts of the Workshop Model on Middle School Student Math Learning. *Christina Chapman, K.B. Sutton Elementary School; Jiyoung Jung, Valdosta State University; Steve Downey, Valdosta State University; Matthew Joseph Smith, Valdosta State University*

Lost in Translation: Narratives of Middle School Math Teachers' Critical Self-Reflections on Teaching English Learners. *Kristina Walshe, California State University - Long Beach; Maiyoua Vang, California State University - Long Beach*

Materiality, Math, and Design: Middle School Students Prototyping Water Conservation Solutions. *Sourabh Garg, University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign; Gloriana Gonzalez, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Michelle Heredia, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

75.073-8. Exploring issues of justice and identity in the mathematics classroom (Table 8). SIG-Socio-Political

Issues in Mathematics and Science Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

A Narrative Study of a CHamoru Math Teacher's Experience with Culturally Relevant Data Science. *Richard Carlos L. Velasco, University of Florida*

Bridging the Gap Between the Design and Implementation of Ideational Resources for Black Mathematics Learners. *Kyalamboka Brown, Stanford University*

Designing and Implementing Math Tasks for Justice: A Bidirectional Framework for Rigor and Belonging. *Eva Thanheiser, Portland State University; Amanda T. Sugimoto, Portland State University; Courtney Koestler, Ohio University; Mathew Felton-Koestler, Ohio University; Simon Byeonguk Han, Portland State University; Molly Robinson, Portland State University*

Math Class is Like Flipping Tortillas: A Latina's Embodied Mathematics. *Marilyn Castro, University of California - Santa Barbara; Rachel Lambert, University of California - Santa Barbara; Rebeca Mireles-Rios, University of California - Santa Barbara*

Somos arte: Enacting a mathematics pedagogy of rasquachismo. *Melissa Adams Corral, University of Texas - Rio Grande Valley; Gladys Krause, College of William & Mary; Luz A. Maldonado, Texas State University*

75.074. AERA Roundtable Session Saturday 11:45 am - Gold 3; Roundtable Session

75.074-1. Pedagogies of Power, Community, and Freedom (Table 1). SIG-Critical Educators for Social Justice;

Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Asian Critical Mentoring as a Third Space of Ontological Resistance. *Robin Brandehoff, University of Colorado - Denver; Daranee Taychachaiwongse Teng, University of Colorado - Denver; Amie Ha, University of Colorado - Denver; John Tan Tran, University of Colorado - Denver; Tom Su, University of Colorado - Denver*

Dog Whistles and White Tears: Whiteness, Power, and the Public Pedagogy of CRT Book Reviews. *Paul G. Sauberer, University of South Florida*

Entanglements as Pedagogy and Method: Tracing Entangled Histories to Imagine Educational Futures. *Margaret Goldman, Rutgers University - Newark*

Navigating Power, Building Community: A Critical Collaborative Autoethnography of a Women of Color Research Collective. *Marlene Brito, New York University; Erika Marte, New York University; Julie Pham, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Neha Sobti, Hofstra University*

Chair: *Robin Brandehoff, University of Colorado - Denver*

75.074-2. Reframing Discourses Toward Educational Justice (Table 2). SIG-Critical Educators for Social Justice; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Affect Capitalism in Elementary School: The Emotional Work of Facing Economic Inequality with Young Children. *Debbie Sonu, Hunter College - CUNY*

Gender Inequality in the Arts: Learning from our Past to Inform Future Interventions. *Tasha Iglesias, Utah State University; Davis Danny F Roylance, Utah State University; Campbell Helton, Utah State University*

Masking As Praxis: Dreaming Disability Justice In Educational Futures. *Chasity H. Mayo, Utah State University; LuEttaMae Lawrence, Utah State University*

Unpacking Equity in the Science of Reading Research: A Systematic Review of Historical Absences, Present Misconceptions, and Future Possibilities. *JaNiece M. Elzy-Palmer, Texas Woman's University; Alexandra Babino, Texas Woman's University; Travis Hubbard, Texas Woman's University*

Chair: *Tehia Starker Glass, University of North Carolina - Charlotte*

75.074-3. Communities of Practice to Center Justice-Centered Teaching and Learning (Table 3). SIG-Critical Perspectives on Early Childhood Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

A Sustained Community of Practice to Transform Justice-Centered Teaching in an Early Childhood Classroom. *Victoria Damjanovic, Northern Arizona University; Jennifer Ward, Kennesaw State University*

De/Humanization in Kindergarten: A Case Study of Classroom Environment in a Neoliberal Context. *Kaellen Williams, Michigan State University*

Pedagogies of Difference: Refusing a Negative Construction of Difference in Elementary Behavior Intervention. *Lindsey Aleeta Lush, Augusta University*

Reimagining Early Childhood Assessment: Learning Stories as a Paradigm Shift in Practice. *Annie White, California State University - Channel Islands; Christine Carducci, Foothill College*

Chair: *Sandra Barrueco, The Catholic University of America*

75.074-4. Schools as Organizations Managing Change (Table 4). SIG-Sociology of Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Embedding Equity-Mindedness in Community Colleges: Organizational Learning through a Statewide Collaborative. *Karin Yndestad, Northwestern University; Johanna S Quinn, Fordham University; Rachel C. Feldman, Shenandoah University*

From 'Ceremonies' to Routines: The Challenge of Embedding Climate Action in New York K-12 Public Schools. *Merav Hayak, Columbia University; Achva Academic College; Ben-Gurion University of the Negev; Dafna Gan, The Open University of Israel; Oren Pizmony-Levy, Teachers College, Columbia University*

From Loose Coupling to Warm Embrace: Declining Enrollment and the Future of Urban Schools. *Alvin Makori, University of Southern California; Pedro A. Noguera, University of Southern California*

Schools' Agency Matters: How Agentic Differentiation Occurs Under Institutional Isomorphism? *Qingqing Li, Beijing Normal University; Qian Zhao, Beijing Normal University*

Chair: *Anderson Neal de Andrade, Rutgers University*

75.074-5. Career and Pathway Exploration in Career and Technical Education and Workplace Learning (Table 5). SIG-Career & Technical Education and Workplace Learning; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Excellent Sheep or Not? University Students' Career Identity in China. *Yixing YANG, The Education University of Hong Kong; Tingyan Wang, Shunde Polytechnic University*

Pipeline to Water Pros: Exploring STEM Pathways to a Career in Water. *Janel Ancayan, California State University - Long*

Beach; James F. Kiesel, California State University - Long Beach

The Work-Based Learning Self-Discovery Model: A Constructivist Grounded Theory. *Michelle E. Bartlett, Old Dominion University; James Bartlett, Old Dominion University; Brooke Rice, NAF; Nicholas Minar, NAF; Kayla Hollings, NAF*

Understanding career goals and career support programming needs of Upcoming Youth: A focus group study. *Catherine Arley, foundry10; Zulma Guasch-Pereira, foundry10*

75.074-6. Latinx Graduate Pathways in STEM and Beyond: Mapping Belonging, Capital, and Cultural Persistence (Table 6). SIG-Latina/o/x Research Issues; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Cultivating Capital: How Latina Graduate STEM Students Promote Their STEM Perseverance. *Yolanda Arciniega, University of California - Los Angeles*

Entre Cartas y Mapas: Exploring Spatial Belonging of Rural Latinx Graduate Students. *Marlene Lopez Torres, University of California - Santa Barbara; Carlos A Fitch, University of California - Santa Barbara*

Familia, Redes, y Research: Social Networks in the Research Journeys of First-Generation Latinx STEM Students. *Katherine Arias Garcia, University of California - Irvine; Gustavo Orosco, Yale University*

Latinx Students and Residents Leveraging Familial Capital in Medical Education. *Nicole Perez, University of Illinois at Chicago; Vanessa Pena, University of Illinois at Chicago; Isabella Perez Pecchio, University of Illinois at Chicago; Sarah Medina-Aguirre, University of Illinois at Chicago*

Chair: *Nicole Perez, University of Illinois at Chicago*

75.074-7. Living Liminality: Navigating Belonging, Resistance, and Care in Immigrant Educational Journeys (Table 7).

SIG-Latina/o/x Research Issues; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Envisioning Equitable Futures and Resisting Legal Violence: Immigrant Youth and Postsecondary Possibilities. *Sophia L. Angeles, Pennsylvania State University*

“¡Mamá! ¡Así no se dice!”: Exploring intergenerational and collective language practices amongst immigrant children and mothers. *Jackson Gzehoviak, University of California - Los Angeles; Micaela Bronstein, University of California - Los Angeles; Flora Zempleni, University of California - Los Angeles*

Reconceptualizing Belonging for Undocumented Latinx Students: A Critique of Integration in Higher Education. *Beatriz Trejo, University of Utah*

Reimagining Belonging in Higher Education: A Conceptual Framework for Latinx Undocuqueer Student Belonging. *Sonny Partola, University of Wisconsin - Stevens Point; Beatriz Trejo, University of Utah*

Solo el Pueblo Salva al Pueblo: Schools and Communities Response to ICE Raids in California. *Martha C. Franco, California State University - Long Beach; Stephany Cuevas, Chapman University*

Chair: *Beatriz Trejo, University of Utah*

75.074-8. Coaching, Leadership, and Organizational Culture in Youth and College Sport (Table 8). SIG-Research

Focus on Education and Sport; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Delivering Setback Training Sessions to a University Sport Team: A Longitudinal Analysis. *Patti C. Parker, Thompson Rivers University; Lia Daniels, University of Alberta; Amber Mosewich, University of Alberta*

Win at All Costs? COVID-19 Protocol Compliance and the Performance Culture of NCAA Coaches. *Leah P. Hollis, Pennsylvania State University; Gala Sofia Campos Oaxaca, Pennsylvania State University*

College Basketball Coaches' Perceptions of University Presidential Leadership. *Sarah E. Stokowski, Clemson University; Chris Croft, University of Southern Mississippi; Eric Sabin, Clemson University; Chris Corr, Clemson University; Michael G. Godfrey, Clemson University*

Coach Education for Youth Development: An Ecological Perspective Meta-Analytic Review. *Longxi Li, University of Washington; Irina Tereschenko, University of Washington; Julie A. McCleery, University of Washington*

Chair: *Antonio Garcia-Bautista, Claremont Graduate University*

75.074-9. Teaching and Teacher Formation: A Systems Thinking in Education Roundtable (Table 9). SIG-

Systems Thinking in Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

A Model of School-Based Agricultural Education Teacher Identity Formation. *Catlin M. Goodwin, Michigan State University; Aaron J. McKim, Michigan State University*

Crafting Coherence through Educational Infrastructure to Support Elementary Science Teaching. *Jonathan L. Hall, California State University - San Bernardino; Yewon Sung, California State University - San Bernardino; Peet Smith, California State University - San Bernardino; Halil I. Tasova, California State University - San Bernardino; Xinying Yin, California State University - San Bernardino*

Teaching Educational Systems as Complex Systems Using Agent-Based Modelling and Conceptual Change Research. *Nathanaël Friant, Université Libre de Bruxelles; Thomas*

Gennen, University of California, Berkeley

Chair: *Kathleen Scott, Pepperdine University*

Discussant: *Linda K. Mayger, The College of New Jersey*

75.075. AERA Roundtable Session Saturday 11:45 am - Gold 4; Roundtable Session

75.075-1. Mathematics Learning for Multilingual Students (Table 1). Division C - Learning and Instruction; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Equity for Multilingual Learners: Long-term English Learners' Opportunities to Engage in Mathematical Discourse. *Teresa Granados, Claremont Graduate University*

Mathematics Instruction in Mother Tongue: Exploring the Impacts of Teaching Mathematics in Nigerian Local Languages. *Kafayat Amoke Adesina, Clemson University; Augustine Owusu Achiaw, Clemson University; Edwin Nii Bonney, Clemson University; Gertrude Arthur, University of Missouri; Ibraheem Abiola Alabi, Lagos State University of Education*

Understanding Unproductive Struggle During Mathematics Discussions in a Linguistically Diverse Elementary Math Context. *Lorelei R. Coddington, Biola University; Stacy Kula, Azusa Pacific University; Jane Sugandi, Biola University*

From Silent to Seen: Making Visible Mathematical Practices in STEM Education. *Esma Nur Kahveci, University of Massachusetts - Dartmouth; Shakhnoza Kayumova, University of Massachusetts - Dartmouth*

Chair: *Jing Wang, University of Nebraska - Lincoln*

75.075-2. Advancing Equity and Access in Educational Systems (Table 2). Division H - Research, Evaluation and Assessment in Schools; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Beyond Ratios: How High School Counselor Caseloads and Time Allocation Shape College Access. *Yue Di, Michigan State University*

Doctoral Motivation and Program Environment in Ed.D. Programs: A Qualitative Study of Student. *Christa Reyes, Florida Gulf Coast University; Jingshun Zhang, Florida Gulf Coast University*

Empowering a New Generation: Evaluation of the U.S State Department's Young African Leaders Initiative (YALI) in Sub-Saharan African as a Future-Focused Educational Initiative. *Joshua Amponsah, Western Michigan University; Mwila Mvula, Western Michigan University; Brooks Applegate, Western Michigan University*

Reimagining Family Engagement: Equity-Centered Tools and

Practices for Systemic School Transformation. *Katarzyna Razynska, MAEC; Karmen Rouland, MAEC; Marianna Stepniak, Mid-Atlantic Equity Consortium; Kailanya Brailey, MAEC; Rita Perez, MAEC*

Validation of an Equity Audit Tool Based on Item Response Theory. *Vo Ram Yoon, Mid-Atlantic Equity Consortium*

Chair: *Anuja Sarda, Clemson University*

75.075-3. Immersive and XR Pedagogies for Presence and Precision (Table 3). SIG-Design and Technology; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Designing Authentic VR Learning for Microelectronics with the TAPPA Process. *Rob Moore, University of Florida; Sophia Soomin Lee, University of Florida; Hyo Kang, University of Florida*

Designing Technology with Empathy: Insights from Students Navigating Mental Health in College. *Emily Carol Espinoza, Kennesaw State University; Yash Gabale, Kennesaw State University; Kanu Priya Singh, Kennesaw State University*

Embodied Engagement in Immersive Learning: Enhancing Presence through Integration of Narrative-based Strategy and Immersive Technology. *Shima Dadkhahfard, University of Calgary; Farzan Baradaran Rahimi, Grant MacEwan University*

Teacher Support in Augmented Reality-Enhanced Science Learning in Primary School Classrooms. *Zong Ran Wang, East China Normal University; Yun Wen, Nanyang Technological University*

Chair: *Ahmed Lachheb, University of Kansas*

75.075-4. Arts based educational research methods and methodologies (Table 4). SIG-Arts-Based Educational Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Cut as Catalyst: Collage-Making as Data Analysis and Representation of "SpiRitual Languageing". *Bianca Gonzalez, McGill University*

More Loongs: A/r/tographically Examining the Issues Hidden in My Art Education Stories. *Mengkai Zhang, University of Victoria*

Humanizing Learning Through Arts-Oriented Community-Building: An A/r/tographic Quilting Inquiry. *Karenanna Boyle Creps, Michigan State University; Anthony Dickson, Michigan State University; Dominic Hateka, Michigan State University*

Chair: *Mindy Roberta Carter, McGill University*

Discussant: *Caroline Pearsall, Teachers College, Columbia University*

75.075-5. Spaces with/in arts based educational research

(Table 5). SIG-Arts-Based Educational Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Reimagining the Gallery as an Inclusive Site of Participatory Arts-Based Research. *Lucius Von Joo, Teachers College, Columbia University; Chris Moffett, Teachers College, Columbia University; Blake Danzig, Teachers College, Columbia University; Emmy Semprun, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Tenting—Creative Enfolding of Space in Educational Research: A Duoethnography by Two Female Academics. *Yen-Ju Lin, Independent Scholar; Pin-Hsuan Tseng, Pennsylvania State University*

The Role of Performing Arts-based Education in the Development of Antiracist Identities in White Children. *Michael Joseph Haverty, Georgia State University*

Chair: *Md Mamunur Rashid, University of Rochester*

75.075-6. Disrupting Power in Qualitative Research: Three Alternative Approaches to Data Collection and Analysis (Table 6). SIG-Qualitative Research; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Worldbuilding as a Way to Imagine Futures: Using Futures Thinking within Qualitative Interviewing. *Ramyia Kumaran, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Layered Re-Storying as a Power-Conscious Approach to Narrative Analysis. *Kemeyawi Wahpepah, Harvard University*

Challenging Power and Repairing Harm: Reframing Member Checking Through Restorative Justice Principles. *Alexander Parker, Johns Hopkins University*

Chair: *Alexander Parker, Johns Hopkins University*

Discussant: *Giovanni P. Dazzo, University of Georgia*

75.075-7. Digital Literacy, Robotics, and Ethical AI in Education (Table 7). SIG-Technology, Instruction, Cognition & Learning; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Learning to Code, Learning to Care: Promoting Ethics and Agency in Elementary AI Curriculum. *Burak Sahin, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Hasan Deniz, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*

Three-year development of digital literacy in children and adolescents: The role of digital activity participation and demographic characteristics. *Min Lan, Zhejiang Normal University; Sisi Tao, Education University of Hong Kong; Qianqian Pan, Nanyang Technological University; Qianru*

Liang, Jinan University; Cheng Yong Tan, University of Hong Kong; Nancy W.Y. Law, University of Hong Kong
Understanding the Impact of a Robotics-based Language Arts Curriculum on Rural Students' Computer Science Self-efficacy. *Hengtao Tang, University of South Carolina; Yingxiao Karen Qian, University of South Carolina; Susan Porter-Voss, University of South Carolina*

Unpacking Fifth Graders' Perspectives on STEAM: Knowledge, Attitudes, Challenges, and Insights From Self-Reported Experiences. *Jillian Powers, Florida Atlantic University; Danielle R. Brown, Florida Atlantic University; Susannah L. Brown, Florida Atlantic University; Ann T Musgrove, Florida Atlantic University*

75.075-8. Cultivating Coalition Through Multiple Literacies

(Table 8). SIG-Writing and Literacies; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Black Girls and Queer Filipinx Youth: A Coalitional Exploration of Body as Literacy and Home. *Anthony Andre Zarate, University of Pennsylvania; Barrett Rosser, Morgan State University*

Cultivating transnational solidarities through co-designed literacy events: Examining the practices of a Mexico-US educational partnership. *Maria Paula Ghiso, Teachers College, Columbia University; Gerald Campano, University of Pennsylvania; Maria Beatriz Pinto, University of Pennsylvania; Gabriela Hargraves, Teachers College, Columbia University; Kelsey Trudo, University of Pennsylvania; Jacqueline Winsch, University of Pennsylvania; Yanil De La Rosa, University of Pennsylvania*

“You’ll become a muslim just like them”: Kosova Youth Bridging Ethnic and Geographical Divides Through Social Media. *Ermal Hoxha, University of Missouri; Robert Petrone, University of Missouri*

Chair: *Nicole R. Misra, University of Missouri - St. Louis*

75.075-9. Evaluating and Validating Measures of Student Learning and Performance (Table 9). Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Comparing English Essay Scoring: LLMs vs. Human Raters. *Youngjin Lee, University of North Texas*

Cross-Cultural Validation of the 2022 PISA Creative Thinking Assessment: Evidence from Five Asian Regions. *Chia-Wen Chen, University of Cambridge; Ji Young Kim, The George Washington University; Yu-Chieh Wu, University of Hawai'i at Mānoa*

Evaluation and Modification of Formulas for Discussion Quality Score. *Chien-Chang Pan, Pennsylvania State*

University; P. Karen Murphy, Pennsylvania State University; Carla M. Firetto, Arizona State University; Jeff A. Greene, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Rachel Miriam Vriend Croninger, Pennsylvania State University

The Callysto Computational Thinking Test for undergraduate students: A psychometric study. Yajie Song, McGill University; Yimei Zhang, McGill University; Hao-Yue Jin, University of Alberta; Chang Lu, Shanghai Jiao Tong University; Connie Levina Yuen, Athabasca University; Florence Glanfield, University of Alberta; Catherine Adams, University of Alberta; Maria Cutumisu, McGill University

Chair: Min Liu, Baylor University

Division and SIG Posters

75.076. AERA Poster Session Saturday 11:45 am; Poster Session

75.076-1. Excellence in Education Research: Early Career Scholars and Their Work Poster Session. Excellence in Education Research: Early Career Scholars and Their Work; Invited Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Posters:

1. The impact of HighScope's teacher professional learning on children's academic achievement during elementary school (Poster 1). *Sammy Ahmed, University of Rhode Island; Lori Skibbe, Michigan State University*
2. Not-So-Free Markets? The Impact of Educational Privatization and Marketization through School Choice on Attitudes Towards Government Taxation and Spending and on Public Finance (Poster 2). *Mark Chin, Vanderbilt University; Arthas Chen, University of Texas at Austin*
3. Deeper Learning through Socially Responsible Writing: A Register-informed Exploration of a Genocide Awareness Unit (Poster 3). *Emma R. Britton, University of Missouri - St. Louis*
4. Analyzing Institutional Characteristics as Predictors of Graduation Rates for Deeper Learning High School Graduates (Poster 4). *Justin Lamar Bryant, Prairie View A&M University*
5. Unveiling Pathways to Higher Education for First-Generation Students through Deeper Learning Opportunities and School Support Structures (Poster 5). *Samantha LeBouef, University of Minnesota*
6. How Teachers Describe Apprenticeship Opportunities in Deeper Learning Schools (Poster 6). *Julianna E. Lopez Kershen, University of Oklahoma*
7. Culturally Responsive Pedagogies as Pathways to Deeper Learning for Recently Arrived Immigrant Students (Poster 7). *Chandler Paton Miranda, Molloy University; Suma*

Cheru, University of Texas at Austin

8. Explore The Interconnection of Deeper Learning Competencies (Poster 8). *Yuxi Qiu, Florida International University*
9. Towards a Broader View of Deeper Learning: Considering a Multimodal Perspective (Poster 9). *Brett Stamm, University of Southern Mississippi*
10. Learning for a Politicized World: Student Reflections on Deeper Learning and Civic Engagement (Poster 10). *Nathaniel D. Stewart, University of Minnesota*
11. How does attending deeper learning schools impact student self-determination and postsecondary education enrollment? (Poster 11). *Yanli Xie, Florida State University*
12. Enacting critical conversations on racial, linguistic, and anti-immigrant injustice: Toward a theory of anti-oppressive discourse in education (Poster 12). *Chris K. Chang-Bacon, University of Virginia; April S. Salerno, University of Virginia*
13. Language, Space, and Demographic Change: Examining the White Space of Dual Language Education in the U.S. Midwest (Poster 13). *Giselle Del Carmen Martinez Negrette, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*
14. Anacostia River Collective: Interdisciplinary Counternarratives to Disrupt Inequitable Pasts and Dream Liberatory Futures (Poster 14). *Autumn A. Griffin, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Robert P. Robinson, Graduate Center - CUNY; Pempho Chinkondenji, University of North Dakota; Channing Jamielle Mathews, University of Virginia; Andres Pinedo, Vanderbilt University*
15. Learning Progression Informed Multi-Agent AI Feedback System for STEM Sensemaking (Poster 15). *Leonora Kaldaras, Texas Tech University*
16. Estimating Distributions and Ranks of Cluster-Specific Effect Parameters: New Bayesian Tools for Value-Added Modeling (Poster 16). *Joon-Ho Lee, University of Alabama*
17. Thriving in Fogaraté: Engineering Ingenuity in Haitian-Dominican Communities (Poster 17). *Greses Perez, Tufts University*
18. The Nurseries of Democracy: A "Holistic Analysis" of Young Students' First Amendment Rights (Poster 18). *Christopher D. Thomas, University of Florida*
19. Do Changes in Teacher Efficacy and Stress Shape Children's School Functioning? Evidence from Child Fixed-Effects Models (Poster 19). *Qingqing Yang, University at Albany - SUNY*

Chair: *George L. Wimberly, American Educational Research Association*

75.076-2. Teacher Agency, Activism, and Leadership - Div K Section 2. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Posters:

20. Contested Terms: Social Justice Teacher Educators' Work in California (Poster 20). *Mayeen Quader, University of California - Riverside*
21. Developing Teacher Leadership: (Poster 21). *James Coaxum, Rowan University; Matthew J. Stier, University of Iowa; Margaret Thornton, Rowan University; Gaëtane Jean-Marie, Rowan University; Joanne Connor, Rowan University; David Lindenmuth, Rowan University; JoAnn B. Manning, Rowan University; Magdalena Martinez, Rowan University*
22. Innovative Solutions: Can a school redesign project support educators in becoming agents of change? (Poster 22). *Emily Anne Lyons, Springfield College*
23. Personal, Proxy, and Collective: The Different Ways Creative Agency Develops to Support Teacher Flourishing (Poster 23). *Ross C. Anderson, Creative Engagement Lab; Kendall LaParo, Research for Action; Gregory Boldt, University of Saskatchewan*
24. "We Were Ready. . . But Not for This": Novice Teachers Reclaiming Purpose Through Critical Professional Learning (Poster 24). *Brianna C. Connors, University of South Florida; Amanda M. Mirabella, University of North Carolina Asheville*

75.076-3. Foundations of Teaching and Teacher Education for Socio-Cultural, Racial, and Intersecting Minoritized Identities. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Posters:

25. Cultivating Critical Love with Preservice Teachers through Stories of Names, Identity, and Belonging (Poster 25). *Shuling Yang, University of Maryland - Baltimore County*
26. Culturally Responsive Teaching and Difference: Possibilities for Innovating Praxis for Teachers of Immigrant Youth (Poster 26). *Nicole Richardson, University of Minnesota*
27. Digging Deeper: Preservice Teachers Attitudes Towards Ungraded Multimodal Portfolio Assessments in a Teacher Education Program (Poster 27). *Amrit Kaur Cojocar, Simon Fraser University; Shaghayegh Bahrami, Simon Fraser University; Pooja Dharamshi, Simon Fraser University*
28. One Hundred Little Fires: How Oakland's Cultural-Historical Landscape Shapes a Special Educator's Pedagogy (Poster 28). *Chris Emanuel Plantinos, Stanford University*
29. Playing with Power: Silence, Supervision, and the Fracturing of Culturally Relevant Curriculum in Indigenous Teacher Preparation (Poster 29). *Kristopher M. Goodrich, University of New Mexico; Heather Sands, University of New Mexico*
30. Shifting from Individualism to Community Collaboration: Advancing Humanizing School Ecosystems through

Emergent Strategies in Education (Poster 30). *Keisha McIntosh Allen, University of Maryland; Kyla Thomas, University of Maryland - Baltimore County; Sakeena Everett, University of Connecticut; Kindel Turner Nash, Appalachian State University*

31. Situating Teacher Education within Multicultural and Global Context – Lessons Learned from Comparative Case Studies (Poster 31). *Huanshu Yuan, Marshall University*
32. Teachers' Culturally Responsive Teaching Self-Efficacy on the Math Achievement of English Language Learner (ELL) Students (Poster 32). *Jaylene Patterson, University of Kentucky; Olukemi Olubunmi Kolawole, University of Kentucky; Shannon O. Sampson, University of Kentucky*
33. Teaching STEM in Ghana: How Cultural and Gender Norms Shape Classroom Equity (Poster 33). *Martin Ako, McGill University*

75.076-4. Global Perspectives on Classroom Assessment. SIG-Classroom Assessment; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Posters:

34. Cracking the Code: Essential Predictors of Receptivity to Instructional Feedback in Higher Education (Poster 34). *Basak Calik, Istanbul Medeniyet University*
35. Exploring the relationships between classroom assessment tasks and formative assessment practices in English classes (Poster 35). *He Yang, City University of Macao; Sihui Yu, City University of Macao; Yiran Miao, Chengdu University of Information Technology*
36. Rethinking Assessment for Well-Being: Global Expert Insights on the Classroom Assessment and Student Well-Being Connection (Poster 36). *Sumaiya Chowdhury, Queen's University; Christopher DeLuca, Queen's University - Kingston; Michelle J. Searle, Queen's University - Kingston*
37. Students' Emotions in Educational Assessment: Insights from Social Media Big Data (Poster 37). *Amir Rasooli, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University; Farhan Ali, Nanyang Technological University - National Institute of Education; Joenathan Halim, Nanyang Technological University*

75.076-5. Snapshots from the Field: Technology-Enhanced Teaching and Learning. SIG-Technology as an Agent of Change in Teaching and Learning; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Posters:

38. AI Predicting Lesson Plans: The Influence of Teacher and Textbook (Poster 38). *Maya Bialik, Boston University; Pelin Jackson, Boston University; Leslie Dietiker, Boston University*
39. A Mixed Methods Case Study on Enhancing CS Knowledge and Coding Skills in Elementary Students

(Poster 39). *Fatema Nasrin, University of Alabama; Jihane Amayou, University of Alabama; Idowu David Awoyemi, University of Alabama; Parastoo Abedini, University of Alabama; Vahid Mousavi, University of Alabama; Mohammad Mohi Uddin, University of Alabama; Feiya Luo, University of Alabama; Amy C. Hutchison, University of Alabama*

40. Digital Tools, Real Voices: What Teacher Candidates Say About Seesaw in Early Childhood Contexts (Poster 40). *Gui Ying Annie Yang-Heim, Illinois State University; Xi Lin, East Carolina University*
41. Pre-service Teachers Learn Life Cycles through Augmented and Virtual Reality: A Case Study (Poster 41). *Christelle Fayad, Texas Christian University; Richard Curby Alexander, Texas Christian University; Hayat Hokayem, Texas Christian University*

75.077. Meet the Editors - Journal Talks Session 3. AERA Sessions; Journal Talks
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

1. Journal for the Study of Education and Development (Table 1). *Alfredo Bautista, The Education University of Hong Kong*
2. Journal for the Study of Sports and Athletes in Education (Table 2). *Cherese F. Fine, Southern Illinois University - Edwardsville; Jeremy T. Snipes, Southern Illinois University - Edwardsville*
3. Journal of African American Women and Girls in Education (Table 3). *Jemimah L Young, Texas A&M University; Eboni N. Bango, Texas A&M University; Bettie Ray Butler, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Abiola Farinde-Wu, University of Massachusetts - Boston; Jennifer Michelle Johnson, Temple University*
4. Journal of Black Language and Culture (JBLAC) (Table 4). *Kahdeidra Monét Martin, Vassar College; Anne Charity Hudley, Stanford University; Kendra Calhoun, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Aris M. Clemons, University of Tennessee; Ramon Stephens, Stanford University; Mia Harris, Stanford University*
5. Journal of Education Policy (Table 5). *Christopher A. Lubienski, Indiana University; Antonio Olmedo, Institute of Education - University of London*
6. Journal of Online Learning Research (Table 6). *Mary F. Rice, University of New Mexico; Michael K. Barbour, Touro University - California*
7. LEARNing Landscapes (Table 7). *Lynn Butler-Kisber, McGill University*
8. Policy Futures in Education (Table 8). *Marek Tesar, University of Melbourne; Sonja Arndt, University of Melbourne*
9. Professional Development in Education (Table 9). *Ken Jones, Professional Development in Education*
10. Research in Educational Administration & Leadership

(REAL) (Table 10). *Koksai Banoglu, The Education University of Hong Kong; Serap Emil, Middle East Technical University; Evrim Erol, Kutahya Dumlupinar University; Ozge Hacifazlioglu, University of California - Berkeley*

11. School-University Partnerships & PDS Partners (Table 11). *Megan E. Lynch, Boise State University; Suzanne L. Porath, Kansas State University; Danielle Sweetman Richoux, SUNY*
12. Teachers College Record (Table 12). *Nancy L. Lesko, Teachers College, Columbia University; George Nantwi, Teachers College, Columbia University; Emily Candaux, Teachers College, Columbia University*
13. Teaching Educational Research Methods (TERM) (Table 13). *Stephanie Anne Shelton, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Kelly W. Guyotte, University of Alabama; Stefanie A. Wind, University of Alabama; Wenchao Ma, University of Minnesota*
14. Technology, Knowledge and Learning (Table 14). *Dirk Ifenthaler, University of Mannheim*
15. The Journal of Educational Research (Table 15). *Mary F. Heller, University of Hawai'i - West O'ahu; Louis S. Nadelson, University of Central Arkansas; Seth A. Parsons, George Mason University; Lisa J. Vernon-Dotson, Ashland University; Ray Reutzel, Utah State University*
16. Race Ethnicity and Education (Table 16). *Lindsay Pérez Huber, California State University - Long Beach*
17. The Educational Forum (Table 17). *Monica Taylor, Montclair State University*
18. Education Law and Policy Briefs Journal (Table 18). *Beverly J. Irby, Texas A&M University; Nahed Abdelrahman, The University of Southern Mississippi; Benjamin P Jankens, Central Michigan University; Daniel H. Bowen, Texas A&M University*

75.078. e-Lightning Ed-Talk Session 17 - Stage 1. AERA e-Lightning Ed-Talks; AERA Ed Talk
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Exhibit Hall A
- Stage 1; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

- Developing Teacher Leadership: (Stage 1, 11:50 AM). *James Coaxum, Rowan University; Matthew J. Stier, University of Iowa; Margaret Thornton, Rowan University; Gaëtane Jean-Marie, Rowan University; Joanne Connor, Rowan University; David Lindenmuth, Rowan University; JoAnn B. Manning, Rowan University; Magdalena Martinez, Rowan University*
- Innovative Solutions: Can a school redesign project support educators in becoming agents of change? (Stage 1, 11:59 AM). *Emily Anne Lyons, Springfield College*
- “We Were Ready. . . But Not for This”: Novice Teachers Reclaiming Purpose Through Critical Professional Learning (Stage 1, 12:08 PM). *Brianna C. Connors, University of South Florida; Amanda M. Mirabella, University of North Carolina Asheville*

Teaching STEM in Ghana: How Cultural and Gender Norms Shape Classroom Equity (Stage 1, 12:17 PM). *Martin Ako, McGill University*

Cultivating Critical Love with Preservice Teachers through Stories of Names, Identity, and Belonging (Stage 1, 12:26 PM). *Shuling Yang, University of Maryland - Baltimore County*

Situating Teacher Education within Multicultural and Global Context – Lessons Learned from Comparative Case Studies (Stage 1, 12:35 PM). *Huanshu Yuan, Marshall University*

75.079. e-Lightning Ed-Talk Session 17 - Stage 2. AERA e-Lightning Ed-Talks; AERA Ed Talk
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Exhibit Hall A - Stage 2; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Cracking the Code: Essential Predictors of Receptivity to Instructional Feedback in Higher Education (Stage 2, 11:50 AM). *Basak Calik, Istanbul Medeniyet University*

Rethinking Assessment for Well-Being: Global Expert Insights on the Classroom Assessment and Student Well-Being Connection (Stage 2, 11:59 AM). *Sumaiya Chowdhury, Queen's University; Christopher DeLuca, Queen's University - Kingston; Michelle J. Searle, Queen's University - Kingston*

AI Predicting Lesson Plans: The Influence of Teacher and Textbook (Stage 2, 12:08 PM). *Maya Bialik, Boston University; Pelin Jackson, Boston University; Leslie Dietiker, Boston University*

A Mixed Methods Case Study on Enhancing CS Knowledge and Coding Skills in Elementary Students (Stage 2, 12:17 PM). *Fatema Nasrin, University of Alabama; Jihane Amayou, University of Alabama; Idowu David Awoyemi, University of Alabama; Parastoo Abedini, University of Alabama; Vahid Mousavi, University of Alabama; Mohammad Mohi Uddin, University of Alabama; Feiya Luo, University of Alabama; Amy C. Hutchison, University of Alabama*

Digital Tools, Real Voices: What Teacher Candidates Say About Seesaw in Early Childhood Contexts (Stage 2, 12:26 PM). *Gui Ying Annie Yang-Heim, Illinois State University; Xi Lin, East Carolina University*

Pre-service Teachers Learn Life Cycles through Augmented and Virtual Reality: A Case Study (Stage 2, 12:35 PM). *Christelle Fayad, Texas Christian University; Richard Curby Alexander, Texas Christian University; Hayat Hokayem, Texas Christian University*

Chair: *David J. Francis, University of Houston*

75.080. Excellence in Education Research Ed-Talk Session (Stage 3). AERA e-Lightning Ed-Talks; AERA Ed Talk
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Exhibit Hall A - Stage 3; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Enacting critical conversations on racial, linguistic, and anti-immigrant injustice: Toward a theory of anti-oppressive discourse in education (Stage 3 - 11:50 am). *Chris K. Chang-Bacon, University of Virginia*

Thriving in Fogaraté: Engineering Ingenuity in Haitian-Dominican Communities (Stage 3 - 11:59 am). *Greses Perez, Tufts University*

The Nurseries of Democracy: A "Holistic Analysis" of Young Students' First Amendment Rights (Stage 3 - 12:08 pm). *Christopher D. Thomas, University of Florida*

Learning Progression Informed Multi-Agent AI Feedback System for STEM Sensemaking (Stage 3 - 12:17 pm). *Leonora Kaldaras, Texas Tech University*

Culturally Responsive Pedagogies as Pathways to Deeper Learning for Recently Arrived Immigrant Students (Stage 3 - 12:26 pm). *Chandler Patton Miranda, Molloy University*

Towards a Broader View of Deeper Learning: Considering a Multimodal Perspective, (Stage 3 - 12:35 pm). *Brett Stamm, University of Southern Mississippi*

Learning for a Politicized World: Student Reflections on Deeper Learning and Civic Engagement (Stage 3 - 12:44 pm). *Nathaniel D. Stewart, University of Minnesota*

Saturday, April 11th, 12:45 pm

Professional Development Courses

76.010. PD26-17 Constructing Skill in Narrative Analysis.
Professional Development and Training Committee;
Professional Development Course
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Plaza I;
12:45-4:45pm
Director: *Stefinee E. Pinnegar, Brigham Young University*
Instructors: *Svanborg Rannveig Jónsdóttir, University of Iceland; Deborah L. Tidwell, University of Northern Iowa; Simmee Chung, Concordia University - Edmonton; Eliza A. Pinnegar, Anchorage School District; Celina Marie Lay, Brigham Young University; Cathy A. Coulter, University of Alaska - Anchorage; Elaine Chan, University of Nebraska - Lincoln; Vicki Ross, Northern Arizona University; Eunhee Park, Texas A&M University; Gayle A. Curtis, Texas A&M University; Michaelann Kelley, Mount St. Joseph University; Cheryl J. Craig, Texas A&M University*

Saturday, April 11th, 1:45 pm

Governance Meetings and Events

77.001. AERA Books Editorial Board: Closed Meeting. AERA Governance; Governance Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 514;
1:45-3:15pm

Chair: *Vichet Chhuon, University of Minnesota*

77.002. AERA Social Justice Action Committee: Closed

Meeting. AERA Governance; Governance Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 513;
1:45-3:15pm

Chair: *Denise M. Taliaferro Baszile, Wayne State University*

Presidential Sessions

77.010. Comedy as a Form of Joy and Rebellion in Times of Crisis. AERA Presidential Session;
Demonstration/Performance

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 409AB;
1:45-3:15pm

Chair: *Sepehr Vakil, Northwestern University*

Participants: *Katherine S. Cho, Loyola University Chicago; Mica Mosley, Black Teacher Equity Project; Saftiya Noble, University of California - Los Angeles; Pedro A. Noguera, University of Southern California*

77.011. Futuring Our Democracy: A Conversation About the Roles of Education, Educational Policy, and Education Research. AERA Presidential Session; Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 404AB;
1:45-3:15pm

Chair: *Sonya Douglass, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Participants: *James D. Anderson, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Vincent D. Willis, University of Alabama; Roy Danovitch, Teachers College, Columbia University; Drew H. Gitomer, Rutgers University; Paula McAvoy, North Carolina State University; Elmer Roldan, Communities in Schools of Los Angeles (CISLA); Janelle T. Scott, University of California - Berkeley*

Moderator: *Sonya Douglass, Teachers College, Columbia University*

77.012. School Boards, Local Democracy, and the Pursuit of Educational Justice. AERA Presidential Session; Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 406AB;
1:45-3:15pm

Chair: *Julie A. Marsh, University of Southern California*

Participants: *James C. Bridgeforth, University of Delaware; Terah T. Venzant Chambers, Michigan State University; Julie A. Marsh, University of Southern California; Briana Mullen,*

Education Justice Academy; Rachel M. Perera, The Brookings Institution; Elizabeth Todd-Breland, University of Illinois at Chicago

Discussant: *Carrie Sampson, Arizona State University*

77.013. Growing Communities for Purpose: Adaptability and Scalability in Education Justice Work. AERA Presidential Session; Invited Roundtable

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 408A;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

1. Community-Based Education Initiatives (Table 1). *Terri N. Watson, City College of New York - CUNY*
2. Youth Participatory Action Research (YPAR) (Table 2). *Danielle R. Filipiak, Michigan State University*
3. Place-Based or Rural Education (Table 3). *Imogen Herrick, University of Kansas*
4. Early Childhood Community Partnerships (Table 4). *Shannon B. Wanless, University of Pittsburgh*
5. Indigenous- or Tribal Nation-led Educational Models (Table 5). *Jingjing Sun, University of Montana*
6. Higher Education and Institutional Change (Table 6). *Katherine C. Rodela, Washington State University*
7. Educational Research and Methodology for Purposeful Scaling (Table 7). *Kevin Kumashiro, Independent Consultant*
8. Educational Technology/AI Education (Table 8). *Tingting Li, Washington State University*

Chair: *Kira J. Carbonneau, Washington State University*

Discussants: *Kakali Bhattacharya, University of Florida; Rita Kohli, University of California - Riverside; Danny C. Martinez, University of California - Davis*

AERA Research and Science Policy Sessions

77.014. School Active Shooter Drills: Mitigating Risks to Mental, Emotional, and Behavioral Health – A Report from the National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine. AERA Science and Policy Sessions; Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 403B;
1:45-3:15pm

Chair: *Dorothy L. Espelage, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*

Participants: *Melissa Brymer, UCLA-Duke University National Center for Child Traumatic Stress and its National Child Traumatic S; Kristen Harper, Child Trends; Anthony A. Peguero, Arizona State University*

Discussants: *Ron Avi Astor, University of California - Los Angeles; Chris Curran, University of Florida*

Committee Sessions

77.015. Aspirations, Achievement, and Attainment:

Unforgetting Structural Barriers. Committee on Scholars and Advocates for Gender Equity in Education; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 301A;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Breaking Barriers: Black Women's Leadership Attainment and Experiences in Predominantly White School Districts. *Kesha Bascombe, Malverne High School*

Breaking the Paradox of Excellence: How Gendered Math Motivation and Institutional Inequality Shape STEM Aspirations Among Top Math Performers. *Wei Wu, Peking University; Congbin Guo, Peking University*

“Math is for Boys, Reading is for Girls”: Implicit Gender-Subject Biases, Academic Achievement, and Course-Taking Patterns. *Jacob Mitchell Rubin, Vanderbilt University*

Signals in the Silence: Black Women Aspiring Deans and the Discursive Disconnect in Higher Education Leadership Recruitment. *Noelle W. Arnold, The Ohio State University; Lori Patton Davis, University of California, Los Angeles*

Chair: *Marlinda Boxley, Bowie State University*

77.016. Division K Fireside Chat: Unlearning Oppression, Imagining Access: Teacher Education Against Racism and Ableism. Graduate Student Council Cosponsored with Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Invited Speaker Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 402A;
1:45-3:15pm

Chairs: *Martha Lorena Hernández Flores, Florida International University; Nallely Gecik, University of San Diego*

Panelists: *Mildred Boveda, Pennsylvania State University; Nirmala Erevelles, University of Alabama; David I. Hernandez-Saca, University of Northern Iowa; Cathery Yeh, University of Texas at Austin*

77.017. Teaching in the Digital Age: Technology, Environment, and Equity. International Relations Committee; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 502A;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

A Financial Reality Check: Economic Capital and AI Use in Education. *Keqi Li, University of Edinburgh*

Bridging the Gap: Teacher Insights on Promoting Digital Literacy in Indonesia's Secondary Education. *Tati L. Durriyah, Universitas Islam Internasional Indonesia; Asep Ropiudin, El-Bukhory Institute; Nurhalimah Siregar, Universitas Islam Internasional Indonesia*

Motivation Matters: A Cross-National Study of Autonomy and

Teacher Satisfaction. *Robert E. Shockley, Florida Atlantic University; Mounir Bourkiza, Florida Atlantic University; Michael DeDonno, Florida Atlantic University; Siaw Yan Li, University of Malaya; Jiang Na; Joko Sriyanto, Yogyakarta State University*

Socioeconomic Inequality in Digital Learning Skills: Cross-National Evidence from Home and School Digital Environments. *Seong Won Han, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

Chair: *Ashley Watson, University of Minnesota*

Discussant: *Sabahet S. Bruncaj, United Arab Emirates University*

International Organization Sessions

77.018. What We Measure, What We Miss: Reconsidering Assessment Across Educational Contexts. International Aligned Organizations/Canadian Society for the Study of Education - CSSE; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum B; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Large Scale Assessment Data Informing Kindergarten Entrances. *Man-Wai Chu, University of Calgary; Karen Fung, University of Calgary*

Which Bundles Matter? Examining Bundled Accommodations and Achievement for Diverse Math Learners. *Pei-Ying Lin, University of Saskatchewan*

Beyond Consent: Queer Lessons on the Limits of Violence Prevention Education. *JJ Wright, MacEwan University*

Teaching what matters about sexuality and gender: Exploring SOGI pedagogy in Canadian teacher education programs. *Julia Helen Sinclair-Palm, Carleton University*

Chair: *Julia Helen Sinclair-Palm, Carleton University*

Division Sessions

77.019. Empowering Promise Communities: A Multi-Method Participatory Action Research Model for Family and Community Engagement. Division A - Administration; Workshop
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, San Gabriel A; 1:45-3:15pm

Chair: *Armen Alvarez, Western Michigan University*

Presenters: *Armen Alvarez, Western Michigan University; Cristobal Rodriguez, Western Michigan University*

77.020. Praxis and Pedagogies of Liberation: Resistance and Re-Existence. Division B - Curriculum Studies; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304B;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Untethering the Youth Carceral State: Reorienting Toward

Decolonial Educational Abolitionism Praxes. *Brian Cabral, University of Texas at Austin; Monserat Vargas, Independent Scholar*

Once-children, now teachers: Theorizing Black and Indigenous Educator Care as Self-Defense. *Anna Almore, University of Michigan*

Decolonial Praxis in a Time of Live-Streamed Genocide: Dialogic Notes from a Global North Classroom. *Sophie D'Souza, Stanford University; Usha Iyer, Stanford University; Pamela Martinez, Independent*

Teaching as resistance: towards an abolitionist and decolonial praxis in university education. *Leila Mouhib, Université Libre de Bruxelles*

Storytelling and Spirals: (Re)storying, (Re)membering, and (Re)visioning for Collective Liberation and Refusal. *Alexandra Allweiss, Michigan State University; Yaa Oparebea Ampofo, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Unifier Dyer, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Olivia Ann Furman, Michigan State University; Utitofon Inyang, Binghamton University - SUNY; Harry Kiiru, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Rachel Lockart, Augustana College; Romina S. Peña-Pincheira, Gustavus Adolphus College; Jessica Reed, Michigan State University*

Chairs: *Jairo I. Fúnez-Flores, Independent Researcher; Ana Carolina Diaz Beltran, University of Texas - Rio Grande Valley*

Discussant: *Nathalia E Jaramillo, Kennesaw State University*

77.021. Tasting Curriculum. Division B - Curriculum Studies; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304A;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

The Taste of Nostalgia: Revisiting There Ain't No Sugar in Cornbread as Curriculum of Place. *R. Ugena Whitlock, University of South Carolina - Upstate*

Taste of Life and Death. *Patrick Phillips, University of Ottawa*

Tasting Education with Chopsticks: A Diasporic Hakka Cuisine. *Nicholas Ng-A-Fook, University of Ottawa*

Re-membering into Tasty Fables, Imagining Taste-y Curriculum. *Zulitazhira Hinojosa, University of Texas - Rio Grande Valley*

Curricular Tastescapes. *Laura M. Jewett, University of Texas - Rio Grande Valley*

Chair: *Zulitazhira Hinojosa, University of Texas - Rio Grande Valley*

Discussant: *Walter S. Gershon, Rowan University*

77.022. Joy, Liberation, and Creativity as Frameworks for Educational Research. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Symposium
Westin Bonaventure, Level 2, Mt. Washington; 1:45-3:15pm

Chairs: *Barbara Thelamour, Swarthmore College; Helenrose Fives, Montclair State University*

Participants: *Justin A. Coles, University of Massachusetts - Amherst; Grace D. Player, University of Connecticut; Joanna N. Ali, North Carolina State University; LaShawn Faith Washington, University of Texas at Austin*

77.023. Motivation in STEM Learning Environments. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, La Brea; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Costs and Benefits: A Comparison of Motivation and Outcomes in Accelerated Community College Math Courses. *Joshua Davis, University of Virginia; Michelle K Francis, University of Virginia; Delaram A. Totonchi, University of Virginia; Emma Huelskoetter, Tennessee Board of Regents; Yoi Tibbetts, University of Virginia; Ashleigh Smith, Chattanooga State Community College; Chris S. Hulleman, University of Virginia*

How do Different STEM Out-of-School Learning Locations Affect Students' Motivation and Interest? A Comparative Analysis. *Ricardo Puppe, Paderborn University; Eileen Reckmann, Paderborn University; Eva Blumberg; Katrin Temmen, Paderborn University*

Inflated test scores through excessive test preparation?

Associations of teaching to the test practices with academic achievement. *Joy Muth, University of Vienna; Marko Lüftenegger, Universität Wien*

Influences of Teachers' Support on Students' Self-regulation in ESL Collaborative Learning: Mediating Role of Students' Motivation. *Barry Bai, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Xuan Zang, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Qingyao Dan, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Hongfang Li, Baicao Yuan Kindergarten; Yuhong Jiao, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Yu Su, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; To Chan, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Miranda Lin, Illinois State University*

Chair: *Jill D. Salisbury-Glennon, Auburn University*

77.024. Situating Growth Mindset across Contexts and Cultures: Experiential, Environmental, and Developmental Influences. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Symposium
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Beaudry A; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Improving Through Effort Shapes Students' Mindset. *Sungwha Kim, Korea University - Brain and Motivation Research Institute; Mimi Bong, Korea University; Sung-il Kim, Korea University*

Transitions in Motivational Profiles of Indonesian Middle School Students. *Yushan Zhao, University of California - Davis; Rongxin Cheng, University of California - Davis; Kali Trzesniewski, University of California - Davis*

Developmental Variations in the Growth Mindset Effect and the Moderating Effect of Growth-Oriented Classroom Practices in Math Achievement. *Tetsuya Yamada, University*

of Pittsburgh; Xu Qin, University of Pittsburgh; Christina Scanlon, University of Chicago; Ming-Te Wang, University of Chicago

The growth mindset meaning system: A cross-cultural comparison between US and China. Yi Wang, Macau University of Science and Technology; Norman B. Mendoza, The Education University of Hong Kong; I Marie Joy Santillana Gallemit, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Ronnel B. King, Chinese University of Hong Kong

Do Creativity-Supportive School Environments Shape Students' Creativity Mindset and Outcomes? Multi-level Evidence from PISA 2022. Norman B. Mendoza, The Education University of Hong Kong; Hyun Ji Lee, Hunter College, The City University of New York; Ronnel B. King, Chinese University of Hong Kong

Chairs: Norman B. Mendoza, The Education University of Hong Kong; Hyun Ji Lee, Hunter College, The City University of New York

Discussant: Ronnel B. King, Chinese University of Hong Kong

77.025. Expanding the Edges of Method: Multimodal, Participatory, and Equity-Centered Innovations in Qualitative Research. Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Paper Session
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Wilshire Grand Ballroom I; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Finding the Edges of Participation: A Case for Multi-Modality as Equity in Research Design. Auralia Brooke, University of New Brunswick

From Empirical Challenges to Methodological Innovation: Intersecting Traditions of Video-based Research for Dual Math Identity. Jialu Fan, University of Minnesota, Twin Cities

From Theory to Method: Ecological Mapping as Critical Qualitative Tool for Visualizing Teacher Identity Development. Xiaohan Yang Zhu, Texas A&M University; Sarika S. Gupta, Bank Street College of Education; Bailey A. Kaufman, Fordham University

Tracing Multimodal and Chronotopic Learning: Advancing Qualitative Methodologies for Studying L2 Professional Socialization in Architectural Design Studios. Min-Seok Choi, University of Louisiana at Lafayette

“You’re Grounded!”: Multi-Methods Exploration of International Medical Learners in U.S. Medical Centers Using Informed Photography. Christine Anne Beach, University of Arizona

Chair: Auralia Brooke, University of New Brunswick

77.026. Generative AI and Large Language Models in Educational Measurement and Assessment. Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Paper Session
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 7th Floor, Hollywood Ballroom I; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Can Large Language Models Generate Reliable Test Items? A Hallucination-Centric Evaluation. Yishen Song, Beijing Normal University; Qinhua Zheng, Beijing Normal University

Divergent Preferences Between Human Raters and Large Language Models in EFL Essay Scoring. Manru Wang, Peking University; Yihan Chen, Peking University; Xiaoting Huang, Peking University

Exploring Large Language Models for Graphical Data Extraction in Single Case Design Meta-Analysis. Yaosheng Lou, University at Albany - SUNY; Mariola Moeyaert, University at Albany - SUNY; Piet Wesling, University at Albany - SUNY; Benjamin G. Solomon, University at Albany - SUNY; Xin Li, University at Albany - SUNY

Landscape of AI Literacy Assessments: A Comprehensive Review of Instruments and Constructs. Lukas Winfield, Education Development Center, Inc.

LLMs as Math Examinees: A Psychometric Analysis on TIMSS to Advance Equity. Lixin(Lizzy) Wu, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign

Chair: Kamal Chawla, University of Maine

77.027. Methodological Pluralism for Comprehensive Evaluation of the Implementation and Impacts of School Security Equipment. Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Symposium
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Los Feliz; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Using Quasi-experimental Methods to Understand the Effects of School Security Investments on Schools and Students. Lucy Sorensen, University at Albany - SUNY; Samantha L. Viano, George Mason University; Antionette Stroter

Web-scraping for School Security Spending. Benjamin W. Fisher, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Samantha L. Viano, George Mason University; Sai Kumar Koneti, George Mason University

Understanding School Security Equipment Decision-Making: A Mixed-Methods Process Evaluation Design. Trevor Fronius, WestEd

Using Youth Participatory Action Research to Better Understand the Effects of School Security Equipment on Students. Meagan Call-Cummings, Johns Hopkins University

Chair: Meagan Call-Cummings, Johns Hopkins University

Discussant: Samantha L. Viano, George Mason University

77.028. Latinx Student Activism, Institutional Power, and Cultural Resistance v2. Division F - Historical Inquiry in Education; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 306A; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

: Sanctuary or Strategy?: Catholic Parish Schools and Mexican Educational Agency in Chicago, 1920–1980. *Sylvia Rosillo, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Diasporic Dreams, Ivy Tower Realities: Puerto Rican Students and the Makings of Home in Higher Education in the 1970s. *Mirelsie Velázquez, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

When Boricuas Are Not Unidos - Intra-Puerto Rican Tensions within Histories of Puerto Rican Student Activism at Yale University, 1972-1975. *Amanda Rivera, Yale University*

Publishing Resistance: The Red Tide's Challenge to School and Police Power in 1970s Los Angeles. *Joanna Torres, Northeastern Illinois University*

Chair: *Christopher J. Getowicz, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Discussant: *Gabriela G. Corona Valencia, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

77.029. Academic Upgrading Students Remember their Pasts and Dream for their Futures through Photovoice.

Division G - Social Context of Education;
Demonstration/Performance
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 411
(Theatre); 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Theoretical Frameworks and Methodology. *Rob Simon, University of Toronto; Ashleigh A. Allen, University of Toronto - OISE*

Context and Participants and Data Sources. *William Edwards, University of Toronto; Melissa Arasin, University of Toronto*

Findings. *Jessica Taylor Charland, Brock University; Samara Rosenbaum, University of Toronto - OISE*

Educational Significance. *Jennifer Emelife, University of Toronto - OISE*

Chair: *Rob Simon, University of Toronto*

77.030. Gender, Race, and Movement: Multi-age Youth Crossing Borders and Divides.

Division G - Social Context of Education; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 301B;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Discrimination at School is Positively Linked to Support for Gender Inequality in Male Refugee Students. *Benjamin Korman, Leibniz Institute for Educational Trajectories; Sophie Moser, University of Konstanz*

Educational Trajectories of Afghan Refugees Through Pakistan. *Ana Kanza Tariq, University of Toronto - OISE*

Imagining Educational Futures Through Friendship: Shaping Migrant Girls' Belonging and Success. *Rocio Garcia-Carrion, University of Deusto; Carme Garcia Yeste, Universitat Rovira i Virgili; Maria Padrós Cuxart, Universitat de Barcelona*

Non-Exploitive Bias in Gendered Educational and Post-School

Transitions of Rural-to-Urban Migrant Young Adults in China. *Linyao Wang, University of Reading; Carol Fuller, University of Reading*

Political Context and Adolescent Refugees' Vocational Education and Training Following Secondary School. *Benjamin Korman, Leibniz Institute for Educational Trajectories*

Chair: *Jie Lin, Shanghai Jiao Tong University*

Discussant: *Alicia Rusoja, University of California - Davis*

77.031. Language and Literacies. Division G - Social Context of Education; Paper Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 303A;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

'Expanding English': Negotiating Creator Identities with Critical Multimodal Literacies in Secondary English Language Arts. *Talia A. Howard Hanna, University of Texas at San Antonio*

Becoming Otherwise through Living Literacies in the In-between. *Xuanya Zhou, University of Florida*

Fostering Black-Latine Solidarity through an Archaeology of Black Language. *Sofia Lisseth Rivas, University of California - Riverside; Alice Y Lee, University of California - Riverside; Dakisha Juarez, University of California - Riverside; Aislin Cortes, University of California - Riverside; Yesenia Mandujano Leon, University of California - Riverside*

Negotiating Identities, Navigating Institutions: A Duoethnographic Exploration of International Instructors' Teaching U.S.-based College Writing. *Scholastika Paul Massawe, University of Massachusetts - Amherst; Carolyn Peterson, University of Massachusetts Amherst*

Chair: *Yetunde S. Alabede, Michigan State University*

Discussant: *Patience Amadu, University of Colorado - Colorado Springs*

77.032. World-making in the Carceral Classroom: Centering Abolition Feminism as an Analytic Lens.

Division G - Social Context of Education; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 504;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

"Babe, I finally feel proud of myself." Formerly Incarcerated Latinas and their Postsecondary Educational Pursuits. *Julissa O. Muñiz, University of California - Los Angeles*

Dear Higher Education In Prison: Letters to an Abolitionist Feminist future for higher education in prison. *Cydney Y. Caradonna, University of Utah*

Borrowing Freedom: Formerly Incarcerated Women and the Gender Violence of the Post-Secondary Education Reimbursement Fund. *Armando Lizarraga, University of Texas at Austin*

An Abolitionist Feminist Analysis of the Racialized Gendering

of Carcerality for Realizing Liberatory Futures. *Casey Philip Wong, Georgia State University*

Chair: *Julissa O. Muñiz, University of California - Los Angeles*

Discussant: *Erica R. Meiners, Northeastern Illinois University*

77.033. Advancing Faculty Competence and Well-Being in the Era of AI. Division I - Education in the Professions; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 8; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

A Coaching-Centered Observed Structured Teaching Exercise (C-OSTE) to Optimize Coaches' Competency in Undergraduate Medical Education. *Celia Laird O'Brien, Northwestern University; Suzanne M. Schmidt, Northwestern University; Sandra M. Sanguino, Northwestern University; Angira Patel, Northwestern University; Brigid M. Dolan, Northwestern University*

Bounded Rationality and Faculty Use of GenAI in Health Professions Education. *Jacqueline E. McLaughlin, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Kelly Womack-Adams, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Zachary Noel, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*

Faculty Experiences with Microlearning in Health Professions Education. *Nicole Puccinelli-Ortega, Atrium Health Cabarrus College of Health Sciences; Amanda K. Burbage, Old Dominion University*

Students Impact Racialized Community College Faculty Sense of Belonging: A Phenomenological Study. *Muhammad Owais Aziz, Old Dominion University; Peggy Gesing, Old Dominion University*

University Faculty AI Well-Being: Social Support, AI Literacy, Tech Self-Efficacy. *Jinyu Wang, National Academy of Education Administration; Weitong Liu, Shandong University*

Chair: *Patricia S. O'Sullivan, University of California - San Francisco*

Discussant: *LuAnn Wilkerson, University of Texas at Austin*

77.034. Debt, Disciple, and Discrimination: Interrogating Inequities Across Higher Education. Division J -

Postsecondary Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum H; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

A Strategy but Not the Goal: Black, Underresourced Enrollees' Perceptions of Degree Worth Through Fugitivity. *Aaminah Long, Indiana University*

Inequities in the student conduct process: An analysis of a state system of Higher Education. *Lucas J Graff, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Federick Ngo, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*

"I Think It's Xenophobic": Toward A New Vision for International Teaching Assistant Policy. *Melissa Hauber-*

Özer, University of Missouri; Sophia Piral Lee, University of Missouri; Hsin-I Yueh, University of Missouri; Kara Starnes, University of Missouri

Late-Life Burdens: Analyzing Student Loan Debt Among US Adults Aged 45 and Older. *Hanyun Cui, Boston University; Jerry M. Whitmore, Boston University*

Chair: *Ashley N. Gaskew, Baruch College - CUNY*

Discussant: *Xiaodan Hu, Southern Methodist University*

77.035. Innovative approaches to improving postsecondary teaching. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum G; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Beyond the Buzz: How Does PD Reshape Online Course Design for Quality Learning? *Alyssa Nguyen, University of California - Davis; Jenny Lee, University of California - Irvine; Di Xu, University of California - Irvine; Michael Hill, University of California - Irvine; Cassandra M.D. Hart, University of California - Davis; Rachel B. Baker, University of Pennsylvania*

How do Teaching Assistants perceive LLM-Generated Feedback? *Xinyi Lu, University of Michigan; Aditya Mahesh, University of Michigan; Mitchell Dudley, University of Michigan; Zeija Shen, University of Michigan; Larissa Sano, University of Michigan; Xu Wang, University of Michigan; Jason Godfrey, Harvard University*

Not All Active Learning Is Equal: Cluster Analysis of Instructional Talk Patterns and Student Engagement in Undergraduate Statistics Courses. *Julie Neisler, Digital Promise; Xin Wei, Digital Promise; Taylor Alexander, Digital Promise; Barbara M. Means, Digital Promise*

Real Time Coaching During Instructional Observation. *Reem Hussein, Texas A&M University; Robin A. Rackley, Texas A&M University*

Chair: *Jonggeun Park, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Discussant: *Michael Brown, University of Michigan*

77.036. Centering Teachers as Policy Actors: Structuring Inclusive and Sustainable Educator Engagement in Policy-Making. Division K - Teaching and Teacher

Education; Structured Poster Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 515A; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

1. Teachers as Policy Actors (Poster 1). *Valerie Richmond, University of Colorado - Denver; Maya Garcia, University of Colorado - Denver*
2. Central Argument (Poster 2). *Valerie Richmond, University of Colorado - Denver; Maya Garcia, University of Colorado - Denver*
3. Roundtable Structure: Creating Inclusive Pathways for Teacher Voice in Policy-Making (Poster 3). *Valerie*

Richmond, University of Colorado - Denver; Maya Garcia, University of Colorado - Denver

4. Reflection & Call to Action (Poster 4). *Valerie Richmond, University of Colorado - Denver; Maya Garcia, University of Colorado - Denver*
5. Integrating Educator Expertise: Collaborative and Inclusive Strategies Aimed at Transforming Policy-Making (Poster 5). *Valerie Richmond, University of Colorado - Denver; Maya Garcia, University of Colorado - Denver*

Chair: *Valerie Richmond, University of Colorado - Denver*
Discussant: *Maya Garcia, University of Colorado - Denver*

77.037. Rewriting the Narrative: Unforgetting the Past and Reimagining the Future of Teacher Preparation. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 9; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Reimagining the Future of Teacher Preparation through High-Quality Teacher Residency Program: The role of school leadership. *Zulmaris Diaz, University of Texas - Rio Grande Valley; GoMee Park, University of Texas - Rio Grande Valley; Lileana Rios-Ledezma, University of Texas Rio Grande Valley*

Evolution of a Bilingual Education Residency Program: Growing and Preparing Culturally Efficacious Bilingual Education Teachers. *Claudia T Garcia, University of Texas San Antonio; Gilberto P. Lara, University of Texas - San Antonio; Belinda Bustos Flores, University of Texas - San Antonio; Juanita Santos, University of Texas - San Antonio; Helyde Adán-Torres, University of Texas San Antonio*

Building Bilingual Teacher Pipelines: Insights from a University–District Residency Partnership. *Catherine A. Lammert, Texas Tech University; Lacy D. Brice, Texas Tech University*

Perceptions of Rural Campus Leaders on the Impact of Year-Long Teacher Residents on Student Achievement in Texas. *Helen Berg, Sam Houston State University; Britine Perkins, Prairie View A&M University*

Chair: *Jennifer Robinson, The Learning Policy Institute*

Discussant: *Jennifer A. Bland, Learning Policy Institute*

77.038. Making the Invisible Visible: Dynamics, Processes, and Outcomes of Research-Practice Partnerships. Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Structured Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 515B; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

1. Sustaining a Research-Practice Partnership with State Leaders (Poster 1). *Hayley Ryan Weddle, University of Pittsburgh; Megan Hopkins, University of California - San Diego*
2. Using AI-Generated Insights to Support Collaborative Decision-Making (Poster 2). *Ha Nguyen, University of North*

Carolina - Chapel Hill; Fabio Campos, New York University

3. Problems of Practice & Practicing Problems: Problems as Sources of Stability and Change in Research-Practice Partnerships (Poster 3). *Carlos Sandoval, Clemson University; Elizabeth A. van Es, University of California - Santa Barbara*
 4. Making Race, Racial Equity, and Power Visible in the Everyday Work of RPPs (Poster 4). *Lindsey J. Kaiser, University of Maine; Amrita Kauldher, Technology Access Foundation; David Goldenkranz, Technology Access Foundation; Patricia Woods, Technology Access Foundation; Heather Lechner, Hayward Unified School District*
 5. Leveraging Diverse Expertise and Collaborative Decision Making in Curriculum Co-Design: Unveiling Structures, Tools, and Practices (Poster 5). *Rossella Santagata, University of California - Irvine; Aakriti Bisht, University of California - Irvine; Yuxi Huang, University of California - Irvine; Taryn M. Williams, University of California - Irvine; Symone Gyles, University of California - Irvine; Teresa Hackey, University of California - Irvine; Hosun Kang, University of California - Irvine; Jennifer J. Long, University of California - Irvine; Sara Ludovise, Orange County Department of Education; Erick Valdez, Orange County Department of Education*
 6. Behind the Scenes: What Does it Take to Leverage Student Voice for Decision-Making in an RPP? (Poster 6). *Brittaney Baker, NashvillePeer; Emily Munn, Metro Nashville Public Schools; Erin C. Henrick, Vanderbilt University*
 7. Aligning Design with Partnership Goals: Transforming Teacher Data Use with Asset-based Analytics (Poster 7). *Seth Van Doren, University of California - Irvine; Abril Gomez, University of California Irvine; Karmelyn Macias, University of California - Irvine; June Ahn, University of California - Irvine*
 8. Making Improvement Continuous: How Network Hub Leaders Plan for the Sustained Impact of Educational Improvement Networks (Poster 8). *Megan Duff, UNC Chapel Hill; Jennifer Lin Russell, Vanderbilt University; Jennifer Zoltners Sherer, University of Pittsburgh; Chris Matthis, Partners for Network Improvement*
 9. Moving from RPP Broker Practices to RPP Broker Practicing (Poster 9). *Diana G. Mercado-Garcia, California Education Partners; Laura P. Wentworth, California Education Partners; Caitlin Farrell, University of Colorado - Boulder; Alison Fox Resnick, University of Colorado - Boulder*
- Chairs: *Paula Arce-Trigatti, National Network of Education Research-Practice Partnerships; Caitlin Farrell, University of Colorado - Boulder*

SIG Sessions

77.039. Intentional AI Integration: Structuring Prompts for

Effective Learning. SIG-Advanced Technologies for Learning; Paper Session

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Beaudry B; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Effective Prompting to Generate Multiple Choice Questions with GPT-4o. *Hedieh Najafi, University of Michigan; Sean Vucinich, University of Michigan; Weiyi Zhang, University of Michigan; Melissa McCurry, University of Michigan*

How do peer feedback and AI-generated feedback differ in features in academic writing? *Junzhu Su, McGill University; Adam Kenneth Dubé, McGill University; LUYAO XU, McGill University; Rob Peregoodoff, TimelyGrader Company; Nikki G. Lobczowski, McGill University*

The Impact of Argumentative Interaction with Persona-Based ChatGPT on Argumentative Writing, Tolerant attitude, and Learning Engagement. *Seonmin Eun, Seoul National University; SEONMIN JIN, Bugil Academy*

Uncovering Student Misconceptions in Data Structures and Algorithms Concepts using Learning Analytics Approach. *Priyadharshini Ganapathy Prasad, University of Florida; Anthony Botelho, University of Florida; Amanpreet Kapoor, University of Florida; Rui Tammy Huang, University of Florida*

The PROSE Model for Designing Artificial Intelligence Activities: Constructive Alignment with Course Content and Objectives. *Hugh Kellam, University of Texas - Arlington; Luis E. Pérez Cortés, University of Texas - Arlington*

Discussant: *Anastasia Shikanova, The Ohio State University*

77.040. Transdisciplinary Perspectives for Critically Analyzing Bilingual Education Systems. SIG-Bilingual Education Research; Symposium

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 309; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Marginalizing Mandarin: A Process-Tracing Study of Dual Language Bilingual Education in LAUSD. *Kevin M. Wong, Pepperdine University; Erina Iwasaki, Teachers College, Columbia University*

“No Seat at the Table”: Inverse Relations of Tight and Loose Coupling and the Sustainability of Bilingual Education in Rhode Island. *Laura Hamman-Ortiz, University of Rhode Island; James Cahan, University of Rhode Island; Jennifer A. Stoudt, Rhode Island Kids Count; Rabia Hos, Southern Connecticut State University*

Language Policy Gatekeepers: School District Leaders and Bilingual Education Availability in New York City. *Ivana Espinet, Kingsborough Community College - CUNY; Maite Sanchez, Hunter College - CUNY; Kate Menken, Queens College - CUNY*

Strategic Framing and Legislative Change: Teachers, Agenda-Setting, and the Bilingual Education Act of 1968. *Leah Durán, University of Arizona*

Chairs: *Laura Hamman-Ortiz, University of Rhode Island;*

Jennifer A. Stoudt, Rhode Island Kids Count

Discussant: *Trish Morita-Mullaney, Purdue University*

77.041. Centering Diversity in Catholic Education. SIG-Catholic Education; Paper Session

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Santa Anita B; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

A Catholic Conception of an Asset Orientation toward Students. *John L. Beltramo, Santa Clara University; Lisa Teresa Archuleta, Stanford University*

A Comprehensive Approach to School Improvement in Urban Catholic Elementary Education. *Charles T Cownie, Boston College; Myra Rosen-Reynoso, Boston College; Audrey A. Friedman, Boston College; Andrew F. Miller, Boston College; Maria A. Moreno Vera, Boston College*

Cultivating Engagement: A National Study Examining Hispanic Parental Engagement in Catholic Schools. *John Reyes, Boston College; Melodie M. Wyttenbach, Boston College; Hosffman Ospino, Boston College; Victoria Berges, Boston College*

Individual or Shared Identity? Perceptions of School Climate in Catholic schools by Ethnic Background. *Daniel Hamlin, University of Oklahoma*

Novice Teacher Induction in a Multicultural Catholic School. *Jenny Yang, St. John's University; Shaoru Liang, Shangping Middle School*

Chair: *Antonio Felix, Loyola Marymount University*

Discussant: *Keisha Goosby, Loyola Marymount University*

77.042. Generative AI in Education: From Hype to Evidence-Based Practice. SIG-Computer and Internet Application in Education; Paper Session

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Palos Verdes; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Beyond the Hype: Understanding How Students Engage with AI Tools. *Olha Ketsman, Northern Illinois University; Bojan Lazarevic, University of Florida*

Effective Methods of Integrating ChatGPT into Student Learning for Achievement: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Jia Chen Liu, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Alan C. K. Cheung, The Chinese University of Hong Kong*

Hype, Help, or Harm? Evaluating AI-Generated Lesson Plans for Civics, Government, and History Learning. *Torrey Trust, University of Massachusetts - Amherst; Chenyang Xu, University of Massachusetts - Amherst; Robert Maloy, University of Massachusetts - Amherst; Kael Pelletier, University of Massachusetts - Amherst*

A Longitudinal Study of Generative AI Integration in Language Teacher Professional Development. *Keyi Zhou, University of Hong Kong; Hongyun DENG, University of Hong Kong; Hong Ching Chan, University of Hong Kong; Chin-Hsi Lin,*

University of Hong Kong

Chair: *Olha Ketsman, Northern Illinois University*

Discussant: *Jewoong Moon, University of Alabama*

77.043. Critical Ethnography to Interrogate, Organize and Imagine Justicia: Learning in, from, with, and amongst comunidad. SIG-Critical Educators for Social Justice; Symposium

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304C;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Recordándose: Reframing Knowledges of Self in an Autoethnographic Workshop for Language Teachers. *Anel V. Rivera Guerrero, Rutgers University*

Just Existing Is Political?: Transborder Organizing Pedagogies at a Community-Based Organization for Immigrant and Workers' Rights. *Chloe Bellows, Rutgers University*

El Limbo de la Bamba: Puerto Rico Educators' Resisting Cultural Erasure in Language Education Spaces. *Sheila Marie Feliciano, Rutgers University*

Resisting Our Erasure: Our Language, Our Histories, and Our Futures. A CPAR Study with Emerging Multilingual Adults from Mexico and Central America. *Amanda Marie Dominguez, Rutgers University*

Chair: *Anel V. Rivera Guerrero, Rutgers University*

Discussant: *Amanda Marie Dominguez, Rutgers University*

77.044. Networks as Sites of Leadership Learning: Failures, Readiness and Absorptive Capacity. SIG-Educational Change; Symposium

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 6;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Novice Principals as Multi-level Change Agents: readiness to lead. *Ruth Luzmore, University of Southampton; Chris Brown, University of Southampton*

The role of absorptive capacity for ICT-knowledge management in schools: Does collaboration matter? *Sandra Fischer-Schöneborn, IU International University of Applied Sciences; Marcus Pietsch, Leuphana University - Lueneburg; Chris Brown, University of Southampton; Burak Aydin, Ege University; Stephen W. MacGregor, University of Calgary*

Leading Educational Change by Learning from Failure in Networks. *Stephen W. MacGregor, University of Calgary; Sharon Friesen, University of Calgary*

Chair: *Chris Brown, University of Southampton*

Discussant: *Elizabeth Zumpe, University of Oklahoma*

77.045. Addressing Issues in Environmental Justice Education through Collective Power in Chicagoland and Southern California. SIG-Environmental Education; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 306B;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Reconnecting Data Visualization to its Anti-Racist Activist Roots through Youth Participatory Science. *Alejandra Frausto, Northwestern University; Daniel Morales-Doyle, University of Illinois at Chicago; Fabio Miranda, University of Illinois at Chicago; Kaleb Germinaro, University of Illinois at Chicago; Valeria Herrera, University of Illinois at Chicago*

Developing Literacies of Land in and through Ethnic Studies. *Christopher Jadallah, University of California - Los Angeles; Nicole Barry, University of California - Los Angeles; Ananda M. Marin, University of California - Los Angeles; Darlene Lee, University of California - Los Angeles*

Situating Trauma, Healing and Well-being as Integral to Community-Based Science Teaching and Learning. *Symone Gyles, University of California - Irvine; Sharim Hannegan-Martinez, University of Michigan*

Cultivating Collective Knowledge, Memory & Resistance in Reinvigorating Environmental Science in Chicago. *Kaleb Germinaro, University of Illinois at Chicago; Michelle Rabkin, Chicago Public Schools; Daniel Morales-Doyle, University of Illinois at Chicago; Alejandra Frausto, Northwestern University; Jocelyn Vazquez-Gomez, Little Village Environmental Justice Organization; Melissa Espindola, University of Illinois at Chicago; Christa Haverly, Northwestern University; Andre Botello, Chicago Public Schools*

Chair: *Daniel Morales-Doyle, University of Illinois at Chicago*

Discussant: *Mindy J. Chappell, Portland State University*

77.046. Land, Language, and Intergenerational Learning: Indigenous Pedagogies of Place, Kinship, and Continuance Across Generations and Geographies. SIG-Indigenous Peoples of the Americas; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 1;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Intergenerational Teaching and Learning in Santa Ana Pueblo: A Study Rooted in Pueblo Methodologies. *Daphne Littlebear, Arizona State University*

Land, and Early Childhood: Participatory Research with Mapuche Communities for Possible Futures in Chile. *Rukmini Becerra-Lubies, Pontificia Universidad Catolica de Chile*

Testimonios of Indigenous Oaxacan Teacher Candidates: Huipil and Huaraches as Acts of Resistance. *Erika D. Garcia, University of San Diego*

Understanding the Relationship Between Learning Diné Bizaad (Navajo language) and the Holistic Wellbeing of Diné Learners. *Tiffany S. Lee, University of New Mexico; Melvatha R Chee, University of New Mexico; James McKenzie, University of Arizona; Wendy S Greyeyes, University of New Mexico; Chenoa Bah Stilwell-Jensen, University of New Mexico*

“Xinachtli pedagogy is a way of being”: Stories from an Indigenous Educator Program in Central Texas. *Pablo Montes, Texas Christian University; Marial Quezada, University of Texas at Austin; Jose Omar Serna, Texas Christian University; Yvette M. Regalado, University of Texas - San Antonio; Leticia Garza, University of Texas at Austin; Toni Moreno, Texas State University; Gabby Campos, Texas Christian University*

Chair: *Patricia Baquedano-Lopez, University of California - Berkeley*

77.047. Critical Reflection of AI Integration in Education. SIG-Instructional Technology; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Level 2, Echo Park; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

When Student Groups Use Generative AI in Collaborative Activities: Exploring Group Discussion and Personal Factors. *Jeongwon Lee, The Ohio State University; Haeun Park, The Ohio State University; Tzu-Jung Lin, The Ohio State University; Thomas Bihari, The Ohio State University*

Human-Generative AI Collaborative Problem-Solving: Critical Thinking Intervention on Reliance Behaviors and Creativity. *Chenyu Hou, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University; Gaoxia Zhu, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University; Vidya Sudarshan, Nanyang Technological University; Fannie Yifan Zhang, Nanyang Technological University; Josephine Leng-Leng Chong, Nanyang Technological University*

Leveraging Bias in Computer Vision AI to Help Teachers learn to Create Bias-Free Learning Materials. *ChanMin Kim, Pennsylvania State University; JungEun Ha, Pennsylvania State University; Brian R. Belland, Pennsylvania State University*

Between Canvas and Code: East Asian Art Educators Reflect on AI’s Role in Teaching and Identity. *Siyao Lyu, Columbia University; Sori Kim, Teachers College, Columbia University; Sung-ah Jun, Sahmyook University; Yadi Liu, China Academy of Ar*

Passive Interaction or Human–AI Collaboration? GenAI’s Impact on Critical Thinking in Higher Education. *Nesma Ragab Nasr, Northern Arizona University; Jennifer M. Werner, Arizona State University; Chih-Hsiung Tu, Northern Arizona University; Tonia F Bauer, University of South Carolina - Upstate; Laura Esthela Sujo-Montes, Northern Arizona University*

Chair: *Hannah M Grossman, University of California - Los Angeles*

77.048. Writing (Righting) Ethnographic Exits: Methodological Insights on Leaving the Field from Elementary Literacy Researchers. SIG-Language and Social Processes; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 501B; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Made Not Only in Words: Reading Child-Researcher Relations through Exit Artifacts and “Are You Leaving?” Letters. *Jon M. Wargo, University of Michigan; Cassie J. Brownell, University of Toronto*

Exit Strategies and Long Goodbyes: Navigating Relational Entanglements When Leaving Classroom Communities. *Haeny S. Yoon, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Drawing Goodbyes: Young Children’s Multimodal Meaning-Making and Relational Connections in Ethnographic Research. *Carmen Lugo Llerena, Teachers College, Columbia University*

“Goodbye / Goodnight”: Making Sense of Ethnographic Exits Through Classroom Rituals. *Beth A. Buchholz, Appalachian State University*

Chair: *Clara Abbott, University of Pennsylvania*

Discussant: *Deborah Rowe, Vanderbilt University*

77.049. Social Issues and the Learning Sciences. SIG-Learning Sciences; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Santa Barbara C; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

AI for Community: Exploring Forms of Relating with Community through Community-Engaged AI Workshop. *Lili Yan, Michigan State University; Marci Hawpetoss, College of Menominee Nation; Caitlin Kirby, Michigan State University; Jennifer Gauthier, College of Menominee Nation; Hara Rania Purboyo, Michigan State University; Julie Libarkin, Michigan State University*

Being a Knower in the Moms for Liberty Podcast. *Tanner Vea, University of Washington; June Jackson, University of Washington; Audrey Harris, University of Washington*

Community sexual health educators’ strategies for cultural disruption in rural, conservative Utah communities. *LuEttaMae Lawrence, Utah State University; Taryn Graves, George Washington University; Malin Scharmann, Utah State University; Indira Adelson, Utah State University; Julie Gast, Utah State University; Cris Meier, Utah State University*

Social conflict as fundamental civic practice: Interactional agonistic democracy in climate learning. *Lynne Zummo, University of Utah; Kaitlyn Kinshella, University of Utah; Emma Carene Gargroetzi, University of Texas at Austin; Indiana Plant, University of Utah; Isabella Prescott, University of Utah*

The social and cultural production of a “misfit”. *Frederick A. Peck, University of Montana - Missoula; Kevin O’Connor, Lafayette College; Christian Lopez Mercado, University of Central Arkansas; Susannah Meyers, University of Montana - Missoula*

Chair: *Malayna Bernstein, University of Toronto*

77.050. Mindfulness-Based Interventions for Teachers:

Mechanisms of Effect and Teacher Outcomes. SIG-Lives of Teachers; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Georgia I;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Pre-Service Teachers' Perspectives about the Healthy Minds Program: Qualitative Insights about an App-Based Mindfulness Intervention. *Summer Braun, University of Alabama; Alison Hooper, University of Alabama; Matthew Hirshberg, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Mark T. Greenberg, Pennsylvania State University*

Preliminary Effects of CARE: A Mindfulness-Based Program for Special Education Teachers. *Jennifer L. Frank, Pennsylvania State University; Andrew T. Roach, Georgia State University; Deborah L. Schussler, University at Albany - SUNY; Sebrina L. Doyle Fosco, Pennsylvania State University; Xiaoxuan Li, Pennsylvania State University; Catherine Jantzer, Pennsylvania State University*

Mindfulness Training Impacts Middle School Teachers' Emotion Skills and Climate in their Most Stressful Classrooms. *Rachel Murray, Pennsylvania State University; Andrew Mashburn, Portland State University; Ellen Skinner, Portland State University; Robert William Roeser, Pennsylvania State University*

The Impacts of Mindfulness-Based Interventions on Teachers' Mindfulness, Mindful Teaching, and Self-Efficacy: A Systematic Review. *Alireza Zareian Jahromi, Fordham University; Joshua L. Brown, Fordham University; Patricia A. Jennings, University of Virginia*

Chair: *Joshua L. Brown, Fordham University*

Discussant: *Patricia A. Jennings, University of Virginia*

77.051. Conducting and disseminating high quality mixed methods research: Exemplars and advice. SIG-Mixed Methods Research Cosponsored with Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Paper Session InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Echo Park; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Sequential Mixed Methods Nested Samples: Selecting Qualitative Participants using Rubrics. *Stephanie Cronenberg, Rutgers University*

When Qualitative Data Are Not Enough: Theory-Informed Quantitizing. *Evan McClintock, University of Colorado - Denver*

Generating Meta-Inferences for Program Improvement: Mixed Methods Integration through Joint Displays for Program Evaluation. *Laura Monkman, University of Michigan; Dhritinut Ratnapradipa, Creighton University; Timothy Guetterman, University of Michigan*

Preparing High-Quality Reviews of Mixed Methods Research Manuscripts: Advice for Reviewers. *Vicki L. Plano Clark, University of Cincinnati; Timothy Guetterman, University of Michigan*

Chairs: *Marcia Gail Headley, University of Delaware; Celeste DC Sodergren, University of Connecticut*

Discussant: *Rebecca A. Cruz, Johns Hopkins University*

77.052. Collaboration in Online Learning. SIG-Online Teaching and Learning; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, San Gabriel B; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Beyond Passive Online Learning: Evaluating a Constructive Engagement Upgrade for Software Engineering Students. *Carla M. Firetto, Arizona State University; Yi-Chun Hong, Arizona State University; Michelene T.H. Chi, Arizona State University*

Exploring The Impact of Peer-Driven Collaboration on Social Presence in an Asynchronous Online Course. *Kwei-Yu Chu, University of Florida; Gail Fornell, British school in the Netherlands; Kathryn Rush, University of Florida; Takiyah Mitchell, University of Florida; Colleen Davis, University of Florida*

Understanding of Undergraduate Students' Interactions in Asynchronous Online Discussions: Social Network Analysis. *Larisa A. Olesova, University of Florida; Daniela Castellanos-Reyes, North Carolina State University; Hajeen Choi, Bowling Green State University; Ayesha Sadaf, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Stacy Gant, University of Florida; Lismarys Cabrales, University of Florida*

Computer Supported Collaborative Learning and Adult Learners in Online Education: The Role of Collaborative Scripting. *Radhika Rajesh Jha, University at Albany - SUNY; Peter Shea, University at Albany - SUNY*

How Intersubjectivity and Time in Course are Correlated within Asynchronous Online Course Discussions. *Barbara M. Hall, National University*

Chair: *Oscar A. Aliaga, University of South Florida*

77.053. Measured Response to Policy Changes. SIG-Politics of Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum I;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Classroom Censorship Policy Diffusion: How a Model Bill Shaped State Policies Across the U.S. *Mallory Lineberger, University of Texas at Austin*

In Wake of "Stop Woke": Two empirical analyses of threats to academic free speech. *Robert A. Maranto, University of Arkansas; Nathan Honeycutt, Foundation for Individual Rights and Expression; Komi Frey, University of Pennsylvania*

Leadership and Governance in Higher Education: A Systematic and Computational Review (2000–2025). *Andres Bernasconi, Pontificia Universidad Catolica de Chile; Francisca Beroiza-Valenzuela, Universidad de las Américas*

(UDLA), Chile; Daniela Véliz Calderón, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile

The Conservative Industrial Complex and Educational Reform. Elena Aydarova, University of Wisconsin - Madison; T. Jameson Brewer, University of North Georgia; Emily M. Hodge, Virginia Commonwealth University; Serena J. Salloum, Ball State University

Discussant: Amanda U. Potterton, University of Kentucky

77.054. Rooted in Relations: Tracing Connections Across Women of Color Methodologies to Reimagine Educational Justice. SIG-Qualitative Research; Symposium InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 6th Floor, Broadway; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Chicana/Latina Feminist Pláticas: Method, Methodology, and Redefining Educational Leadership. Ana M. Segoviano, Twin Rivers Unified School District

A Convivir: Practicing Solidarity as Researcher through Chicana/Latina Feminist Testimonios. Ana Farina de Ramirez, Vacaville Unified School District

Braiding Culturally-Rooted Methodologies: Communal Healing, Freedom Dreaming Circles. LaToya Jackson, Sierra College

“Born under the rising sign of social justice”: Becoming an Anticolonial Scholar-Educator. Freshta Gran Guzman, Fairfield-Suisun Unified School District

Chair: Sheeva Sabati, California State University - Sacramento

Discussants: Chrissy Hernandez, California State University - Monterey Bay; Sheeva Sabati, California State University - Sacramento

77.055. The Ethics of Strategic Framing in Queer/Trans* Research: Protection, Access, and Transformation. SIG-Queer Studies; Symposium Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Los Cerritos; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

The Ethics of Strategic Framing in Queer/Trans* Research: Protection, Access, and Transformation. Shanna Peeples, West Texas A&M University; Em Bowen, University of Arizona; Ferial Pearson, University of Nebraska - Omaha; Jason Laker, San José State University

Strategic IRB Navigation in Conservative Contexts: Protective Language and Community Partnership in Queer/Trans* Research. Shanna Peeples, West Texas A&M University

Literacy of Necessity: Graduate Student Survival Knowledge in Hostile Institutional Climates. Em Bowen, University of Arizona

Intersectional Approaches to Strategic Framing: Protecting BIPOC Queer Researchers and Communities. Ferial Pearson, University of Nebraska - Omaha

Protective Interference: Administrative Allyship in Practice for Community-Protective Research. Jason Laker, San José

State University

Chair: Jason Laker, San José State University

Discussants: Ferial Pearson, University of Nebraska - Omaha; Em Bowen, University of Arizona; Shanna Peeples, West Texas A&M University

77.056. Brothers in the Academy: Critical Dialogues on Black Maleness, Masculinity, and Manhood in Education. SIG-Research Focus on Black Education; Symposium Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 506; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Interrogating Conceptions and Perceptions of Black Maleness, Masculinity, and Manhood in Education and Society. Jawanza Kalonji Rand, Teachers College, Columbia University; Christopher E. Darby, ARE-LO Strategies

The Fire This Time: Surviving and Thriving as a Black Man in the Crosshairs of the Academy. Christopher E. Darby, ARE-LO Strategies

Lifting as We Climb: An Exploration into Black Men's Journey in Higher Education Leadership. Sandile Chad Manzini, Rutgers University

Educational Anti-Black Misandry: Social Science Constructions of Black Male Students, 1970s-2000s. Taharka Anderson, University of Texas at Austin

Chair: Ira E. Murray, Vanderbilt University

Discussant: Timothy K. Eatman, Rutgers University - Newark

77.057. Considering the Interplay between Generative AI and the Mathematics Classroom. SIG-Research in Mathematics Education; Paper Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum A; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Adaptation in AI-Generated Mathematics Feedback: Empirical Validation of AI's Feedback Patterns. Amanda Reinsburo, Drexel University; Cindy Yovanov, Drexel University; Jason Silverman, Drexel University

Integrating AI Chatbot Mentoring into Problem Posing-Based Learning: Exploring Mathematical Thinking and Student Engagement. Hee-Jeong Kim, Korea University; Hayeon Jung, Korea University

Investigating mathematics-teacher-AI partnerships in the classroom: Emergent tensions in the didactic contract. Anthony Matranga, California State University - San Marcos; Traci Jackson, California State University - San Marcos

Mathematics Teacher Interaction Styles with Generative Artificial Intelligence: Personalization Approaches and Problem Quality. Theodora Beauchamp, Southern Methodist University; Candace A. Walkington, Southern Methodist University; Tiffini Pruitt-Britton, American Institutes for Research

Rethinking Research Priorities in GenAI Mathematics

Education Through Systematic Review Analysis. *Eunmi Joung, Utah Valley University; JaeHwan Byun, Wichita State University*

Chair: *Theodore Chao, California State University - Fullerton*
Discussant: *Socorro Orozco, California State University - Los Angeles*

77.058. Ethical Engagement, STEM Programs, and Application of Machine Learning Techniques in Evaluation Research. SIG-Research on Evaluation; Paper Session

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Los Feliz; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

A Scoping Review of Machine Learning and Natural Language Processing Applications in Evaluation Studies. *Ibrahim Osumanu, University of Connecticut; Bianca Montrosse-Moorhead, University of Connecticut; Kylie Anglin, University of Connecticut; Christopher H. Rhoads, University of Connecticut*

Broadening Participation in STEM Programs: Challenges and Proposed Solutions. *Neelakshi Rajeev Tewari, Arizona State University; Tiffany Lee Smith Tovey, University of North Carolina - Greensboro; Ayesha Boyce, Arizona State University; Roya Fathalizadeh, Arizona State University; Seoyoung Lim, Arizona State University*

From Data Extraction to Ethical Engagement: The Town Hall Model in Participatory Evaluation. *Nicole K. Weinberg, Texas Christian University; Gabriel S. Huddleston, Texas Christian University; Garrison Daly, Texas Christian University; Chelsea Verrette, Texas Christian University; Jason David Manriquez, Texas Christian University; Marnie Foster, Texas Christian University*

From Extraction to Authentic Dialogue: Insights from Participatory Case Studies & the DATA-DATA Model in Evaluation. *Tiffany Lee Smith Tovey, University of North Carolina - Greensboro; Ayesha Boyce, Arizona State University; Neelakshi Rajeev Tewari, Arizona State University*

Discussant: *Bismark Wiafe Bimpong, Ohio University*

77.059. Mothering as Methods: Centering Care, Storying Experience, and Re-envisioning Knowledge in Education.

SIG-Research on Women and Education; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 303B;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Reframing Academic Work through Maternal Epistemologies: A Collective Autoethnography of (M)othering in North America. *Xiaoxiao Du, University of Manitoba; Emma Xing Chen, Western Washington University; Ying Xiong, Pennsylvania State University*

A Strength-Based Narrative Inquiry into the Educational Migration and Intersectional Identities of a Chinese Motherscholar. *Ying Xiong, Pennsylvania State University*

Mothering as Epistemology: Dismantling the Traditional Framework for Parental Involvement. *Sudhashree Girmohanta, University of Toronto - OISE*

Teenage Motherhood: Caring Practices as Counternarratives. *Esther Maeers, University of Regina*

Chairs: *Ying Xiong, Pennsylvania State University; Emma Xing Chen, Western Washington University*

Discussant: *Maria Cioe-Pena, University of Pennsylvania*

77.060. Culturally & Linguistically Responsive Science Teaching. SIG-Science Teaching and Learning; Paper Session

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, San Fernando; 1:45-

3:15pm

Participants:

Using Teacher Experiences to Examine Complexities of Culturally Responsive Instruction. *Josie Melton, Western Washington University; Sarah Voss, Western Washington University; Deborah Hanuscin, Western Washington University*

Bridging Language Gaps: Middle School Science Teachers' Practices with Diverse Emergent Bilinguals During Science Instruction. *Samuel Katende, University of Houston; Sissy S. Wong, University of Houston; Maria Alexandra Walsh, University of Houston; Jie Zhang, University of Houston; Hien Thi Tran, University of Houston; Raju Ahmmed, University of Houston; Laveria Hutchison, University of Houston; Elisa M. Holcomb, University of Houston; Donna Stokes, University of Houston*

Moving Forward: Taking Action for the Future through Culturally Responsive Science Teaching. *Jamie Wallace, American Museum of Natural History; Elaine Howes, American Museum of Natural History; Steven Riccio, American Museum of Natural History; Aline Gjelaj, St. Bernard's School; Melanie Hopkins, American Museum of Natural History*

"From Ninja Turtles to Tree Branches:" How Science Teacher Educators Engage with Culturally Sustaining Pedagogy through Objects and Stories. *Wesam M. Salem, University of Memphis; Rachel Diane Askew, Appalachian State University; Susan N. Nordstrom, University of Alabama; Maysa Safi, Southwest Tennessee Community College*
Multimodal Composing in Secondary Science. *Amber W. Deig, University of Southern Mississippi*

77.061. Advancing Justice in Multilingual Education in the United States: Access, Belonging, and Translanguaging.

SIG-Second Language Research; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 7;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Attention Gentrification in Portuguese-English One-Way World-Language-Immersion Classrooms: Listening to Brazilian Reclassified English Learners. *Juan A. Freire,*

Brigham Young University; Rose Renee Whitney, Brigham Young University

Grappling with translanguaging as middle and high school science teachers: Honoring multilingual learners' linguistic repertoires. *Melissa Arabel Navarro, San Diego State University; Maraliz Fischler-Barraza, San Diego State University; Bianca Andrade, Harden Middle School; David Toscano, Otay Ranch High School*

Increasing Access to College and Career Preparation for Multilingual Learners in Community College. *Kylie A. Kenner, University of California - Santa Cruz; George C. Bunch, University of California - Santa Cruz; Benjamin M. James, University of Delaware*

Learning on the Margins: Newcomer Youth Navigating Additive School Spaces. *Kristen McInerney, RTI International; Jordan Corson, Stockton University*

Multimodal Approaches to Instructing Multilingual Learners of Less-commonly Taught Languages: An Interpretive Phenomenological Analysis. *Noelle Hye Seung Roubinek, University of Minnesota; Alexander Fukin Tang, University of Hawai'i at Manoa*

Chair: *Shuzhan Li, Ithaca College*

Discussant: *Nicole King, University of Rhode Island*

77.062. From Past to Present: A Wide Lens Look at Self-Study of Teacher Education. SIG-Self-Study of Teacher Education Practices; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 10; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Relational Pedagogy and Program Stewardship in Precarious Times: A Self-Study of Justice-Focused EdD Leadership. *Barbara A. Henderson, San Francisco State University; Violet Ballard, San Francisco State University; Christopher J. Collins, Skyline College; Alesha Marie Sohler, San Francisco State University*

Self-Study as an Equity Practice: Enacting Social Justice Through the Research Process. *Adrian D. Martin, New Jersey City University*

Self-Study in Higher Education: Insights from a Three-Decade Methodological Review. *Wei Liao, Beijing Normal University; Weiran Wu, Southwest University; Rui Yuan, University of Macau; Zhaoxuan Wang, University of Macau*

Teaching the Past with Purpose: A Collaborative Self-Study of Practice and Preservice Engagement. *Bevin Etheridge, Boise State University; Jennifer L. Snow, Boise State University; Megan E. Lynch, Boise State University*

Chair: *Mark M. Diacopoulos, Pittsburg State University*

Discussant: *Valerie A. Allison, Susquehanna University*

77.063. Embodied, Multiscalar, and Mediated Translanguaging Across Spaces, Identities, and Technologies. SIG-Semiotics in Education: Signs, Meanings and Multimodality; Paper Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 501C; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

ChatGPT said: Becoming Multilingual Experts: Skilled Action in a Virtual Reality Language Learning Environment. *Dongping Zheng, University of Hawai'i at Manoa; Jin Dong, Princeton University*

Embodied CLIL in English-medium nursing education: An organicist-procedural translanguaging approach to thematic patterns co-construction. *Yiqi Liu, The Education University of Hong Kong*

Learning Through Language and Culture Using Semiotics. *Tala M. Karkar Esperat, Eastern New Mexico University*

Making and Using "Quiet Student" Identities in an English-Medium Classroom: A Translanguaging and Flow Perspective. *Gengqi Xiao, University of Wisconsin-Madison*

Reconceptualizing the L2 Writing Process: Human-GenAI-Mediated Feedback through Ecological Language Competencies. *Lu Xi, University of Georgia; Qinghua Chen, The Education University of Hong Kong*

Chair: *Amir Michalovich, University of Manitoba*

77.064. Theorizing Social Studies Education from Below: Civic Knowledge, Praxis, and Possibility from Los de Abajo. SIG-Social Studies Research; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Atrium II; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Rasquache Civic Movidas: The role of humor, play, and resistance in civic practices. *José I. Valdez, Texas A&M University; Jasmin Patron-Vargas, Texas A&M University*
Jeitinho Brasileiro as as Pedagogical Praxis Inherited Epistemology in Social Studies Education. *Carolyn Silva, University of Nevada - Reno*

Lessons from Rastafari and Reggae: Teaching Pro-Blackness and Black Joy in Social Studies Classrooms. *Tianna Dowie-Chin, University of Georgia*

Seguimos en La Brega: How the concept of "La Brega/Bregando" can be used as an analytic tool in analyzing (social studies) teacher practice. *Claribel González, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

The Kwaa: Scraps as Speculative Social Studies for Teachers' Preparation. *Danielle Charlemagne, University of Georgia*

Chair: *Carolyn Silva, University of Nevada - Reno*

Discussant: *Timothy Monreal, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

77.065. Immersive and Experiential Learning with Simulations. SIG-Technology as an Agent of Change in Teaching and Learning; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Georgia II; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

How Generative AI Teaching Simulations Can Support Elementary Preservice Teachers' Elicitation of Student

Thinking. *Heather Jorgenson, ETS; Jamie N. Mikeska, Educational Testing Service*

Role-Play Simulation with AI in Education: Historical Foundations, Current Trends, and New Frontiers. *Rong Ren, Texas A&M University; Leyang Xu, Texas A&M University; Huixin Zhang, Texas A&M University; Yuling Zhuang, Texas A&M University; Zhengzhong Tu, Texas A&M University*

Simulating Change: Preparing Teacher Candidates for Politicized Classroom Contexts through Decision-Based Simulations. *Gretchen F. McAllister, Northern Arizona University; Hoda Harati, Towson University*

Chair: *Hsiao-Ping Hsu, Dublin City University*

Discussant: *Chih-Pu Dai, Texas A&M University*

77.066. Human–AI Collaboration for Enhanced Interaction, collaboration and creativity. SIG-Technology, Instruction, Cognition & Learning; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, San Gabriel C; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Assessing the Impact of Substituting Interaction Types: An Empirical Study of the Interaction Equivalency Theory. *Scott A. Hauert, Phoenix College; Tian Luo, Old Dominion University*

Can Gen AI Improve Low-Performance Students' Creativity? A Quasi-Experimental Study Based on Chinese Samples. *Yiran Cui, Shandong University; Meng Li, China National Academy of Educational Sciences*

Exploring Human–AI Collaboration Patterns in Design Problem Solving. *Yingxue Liu, The Education University of Hong Kong; Shurui Bai, The Education University of Hong Kong*

Home Environment and Students' Creative Thinking: An Educational Data Science Analysis of PISA 2022. *Xi Wang, New York University; Yuyang Shen, University of North Texas*

Using Epistemic Network Analysis to Examine Interaction, Collaboration and Content Creation in the Scratch Online Community. *Seung B. Lee, Pepperdine University*

Chair: *Mandana Delavari, University of Houston*

Discussant: *Chaewon Kim, Florida State University*

77.067. A College and Career Nexus That Promotes Access for All Marginalized Students. SIG-Urban Learning, Teaching, and Research; Demonstration/Performance
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 2; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Racism, Resistance, and Emancipatory Praxis: Counter-Narratives of a Family of AAPI Educators in Urban Contexts. *Katrina Liu, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*
Reimagining College Access: Centering Youth Wisdom and Aspirational Capital Beyond the Debt. *Wendy Morrison-*

Cavendish, University of Miami; Deborah A. Perez, University of Miami; Kaitlyn Casanas, University of Miami

The 'I' in Africa: African-American Students' Explorations of Black Identity through Travel in Ghana. *Cathryn A. Devereaux, Drew University*

Understanding The Relationship Between STEM and A-G Completion Rate At DASS High Schools And Traditional Public High Schools in California. *Anthony Peña, California State Polytechnic University - Pomona*

Unforgetting College Access: TRIO Programs and the Preparation of First-Generation Women of Color. *Aminah Crawford, Texas A&M University*

Chair: *Sheree Nicole Alexander, Atlantic City School District*

77.068. The Productive (In)actions of Do-Nothing Literacies.

SIG-Writing and Literacies; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum J; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Upholding Children's Rights to Literacy in One Japanese Preschool. *Daniel E. Ferguson, George Mason University*

Play as a Critical Participant With/in a First-grade Literacy Assemblage. *Kimberly Lenters, University of Calgary*

Gettin' Show Ready in the Livestock Barn: Refusing Neoliberalism Through Multispecies Kinships. *Jaye Johnson Thiel, University of Alabama*

"Inconvenient" Book Choices: Becoming Un/censored. *Bessie P. Dernikos, Florida Atlantic University; Alyssa Niccolini, Goethe University Frankfurt*

Chair: *Daniel E. Ferguson, George Mason University*

Discussant: *Gail M. Boldt, Pennsylvania State University*

Division and SIG Roundtables

77.069. AERA Roundtable Session Saturday 1:45 pm;
Roundtable Session

77.069-1. Artificial Intelligence and Innovation in Counselor Education (Table 1). Division E - Counseling and Human Development; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

AI in Higher Education Mental Health: A Systematic Review through the Digital Health Equity Lens. *Maricela Ivette Avalos, California State University - Los Angeles; Zixin Zheng, California State University - Los Angeles; Jacquelyn Tsui, California State University - Los Angeles; Sarah Manchanda, California State University - Los Angeles*
Assessing the Effectiveness of an AI-Based Learning Counseling Mentoring Program for English Underachievers. *Juhyeon Park, Seoul National University; Sungkyung Park, Seoul National University; Cheolil Lim, Seoul National*

University

Enhancing Counselor Education with AI Chatbots: Attitudes toward Artificial Intelligence and Counseling Skill Development. *Eunae Han, University of Texas - El Paso; Pei-Ling Hsu, University of Texas - El Paso*

77.069-2. From the University to the Neighborhood: Activism and Mobilization to Remember, Resist, and Reimagine Educational Justice and Renewal (Table 2). Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

A Historical Account of an Undocumented Student-Led Organization at UC Davis. *Miriam G. Delgado, University of California - Riverside*
From the Classroom to the Street: The Politics of Space in Sudan's Uprisings and Revolution. *Sara Nouri, The Child Advocacy Center of Greater Rochester*
Protest and the Democratic University: A Historical-Sociological Inquiry into Campus Activism and Institutional Power, 1945–2024. *Yi Wu, Pennsylvania State University*
Servingness as Embodied Ethos at a Fronterizx Hispanic-Serving Institution. *Christina Convertino, University of Texas - El Paso; Lucia Dura, University of Texas - El Paso; Jesus Cisneros, University of Texas - El Paso; Isaac Frausto-Hernandez, University of Texas - El Paso*
Chair: *Rowhea M. Elmesky, Washington University in St. Louis*

77.069-3. Housing Instability: Roots, Redlining and Academic Disruption (Table 3). Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Burdens of Choice and Closure: Oral Histories of San Antonio Schooling. *Habiba Noor, Trinity University; Maria Aleman, Trinity University*
Redlining Educational Spaces: Advancing a Critical Analytical Framework for Disclosing Racialized Educational Spaces. *William Francis Gates, Boston Architectural College; Noor Ali, Northeastern University*
Rooted in Place: Understanding Teacher Housing Initiatives in Context—A Racial and Spatial Analysis. *Jackquelin Bristol, University of Colorado - Boulder*
Temporary, Not Trivial: Measuring Differing Associations Between Unhoused Students' Temporary Housing Accommodations and Their Learning. *Fabian Barch, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

77.069-4. Latinx Communities and the Navigation of Contested Educational Space (Table 4). Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 1:45-

3:15pm

Participants:

A “Living” Chicana/o/x History: Confronting Racial Injustice by Centering Place-Based Knowledges and Histories in Secondary Curriculum. *Arturo Nevárez, California State University - Stanislaus*
Educating Through Uncertainty: The Impact of Immigration Enforcement on the Nation's Schools From 2017 to 2025. *Maria R. Coady, North Carolina State University; Alejandro Amaya, North Carolina State University; Patricia Shimura Ambrosio, North Carolina State University; Zaina Dali, North Carolina State University; Xinyan Fu, North Carolina State University; Hakima Harris, North Carolina State University; Majid Komasi, North Carolina State University; Rocio López Caicedo, North Carolina State University; Kerianne Peadar, North Carolina State University*
Possibilities for Civic Education: The Civic Life of One Latina Girl in Los Angeles. *Claudia Diera, California State University - Los Angeles*
Raciolinguistic Chronotopes of Resistance in School Interactions: Testimonios from Latinx Mothers in the U.S. South. *Mariana Lima Becker, University of Georgia*

77.069-5. Approaches and Challenges to Youth Health and Well-Being (Table 5). SIG-Adolescence and Youth Development; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Beyond Entertainment: Adolescents, Trauma, and the Social Meaning of School Fight Recordings. *Lijuan Shi, Bard High School Early College; Kym Sturdivant, DC Public Schools; arahv Magine, Bard High School Early College DC; Nia Arrington, Bard High School Early College DC; Jiaxuan Zong, University of Maryland*
Longterm Health and GPA. *Christian Vazquez, University of Texas - Arlington; Carlos Chavez, University of Minnesota; Michael C. Rodriguez, University of Minnesota*
Mind Mapping as an Embedded Reflection Tool in a Positive Youth Development Program. *Anne Katherine Armstrong, Worcester State University*
The Relationship Between Play and Creativity Among Elementary School Students. *Tzu-Erh Yang, National Cheng Kung University; Yu-Shan Ting, National Chung Hsing University; I-Hsuan Chen, National Cheng Kung University; Hsu-Chan Kuo, National Cheng Kung University*
Why I No Longer Wish to Attend School? A Narrative Inquiry on Middle School Students. *peixuan li, Beijing Normal University; Qian Zhao, Beijing Normal University*

77.069-6. Mentoring for Teacher Preparation and Practitioner Development (Table 6). SIG-Mentorship and Mentoring Practices; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 1:45-

3:15pm

Participants:

Reclaiming the Self in Community: Peer Mentoring and Narrative Agency Among Novice Language Teachers. *Shannon Athey, West Chester University of Pennsylvania*

“The real deal”: Mentoring English as a Second Language pre-service teachers. *Maria Guzman Antelo, Rhode Island College*

Title: From Teacher to Mentor: Rural Educators' Perceptions of Their Mentoring Preparation and Support. *Amber Wagon, Stephen F. Austin State University; Ronda McClain, Stephen F. Austin State University; Adam Akerson, Stephen F. Austin State University; Mark S. Montgomery, Stephen F. Austin State University*

Kitchen Table Mentorship: Black Feminist Dialogues on Radical Care, Resistance, and Academic Thriving. *Dawn Stephens Jenkins, University of Texas - Arlington; Ericka Roland, University of Texas - Arlington*

Chair: *Robin Brandehoff, University of Colorado - Denver*

77.069-7. Culture and Climate in Higher Education (Table 7).

SIG-School Community, Climate, and Culture; Roundtable Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Affirmative Action No More: Unpacking UC Regent Response to Special Policy 1 (SP-1) & Special Policy 2 (SP-2). *Tim Herd, University of California - Los Angeles*

Between “Home and Homeland.” The Educational Experiences of Ghanaian International Students in U.S. Universities. *Peter Kofi Dabie, Miami University (OH); Joel R. Malin, Miami University (OH)*

Fostering a Sense of Belonging through a Self-Awareness Undergraduate Curricular Intervention. *Nishala Iroshini Silva, Texas Christian University; David E. Allen, Texas Christian University; Frank Hernandez, Texas Christian University*

The Quest for Belonging: Navigating University and Workforce Expectations While Being Transgender and/or Gender Non-Conforming. *Martin Van Boekel, University of Minnesota; Wilhelm Reign Boomer, University of Minnesota; Annabel Bruton, University of Minnesota; Chris Steadman, University of Minnesota; Shelby Weisen, University of Minnesota; Varun Athilat, University of Minnesota*

77.069-8. Educational Collaborations to (Re)Imagine Critical Studies in Education: Working Towards New Visions for Education Research (Table 8).

SIG-Critical Issues in Curriculum and Cultural Studies; Roundtable Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

From Interdisciplinarity to Multidisciplinarity in Critical

Education Research: Complexity at Every Level. *Jessica Masterson, Washington State University - Vancouver*

Indigenous Futurities and Collective Continuance: New possibilities for educational research. *Stephany RunningHawk Johnson, Washington State University*

Moving Criticality Beyond the Academy: Equipping Educators with Tools to Support Student Critical Consciousness Development. *Anya Sheftel, Washington State University*

Re/claiming Our Senses: Re/imagining Teacher Education and Professional Growth. *T. Francene Watson, Washington State University*

Indigenous Research Methodologies and Methods – Storywork and Storying – Connecting Meaning Through Weaving and Beading Metaphors. *Angel K Sobotta, Washington State University*

Chair: *John J. Lupinacci, Washington State University*

77.069-9. Decolonizing Pedagogies, Teachers And Uncertain Times (Table 9).

SIG-Decolonial, Postcolonial, and Anti-Colonial Studies in Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

From Alienation to a Pedagogy of Hope: Educating for Global Citizenship through English Language in Post-colonial Algeria. *Fadhila Hadjeris, University of California - Los Angeles*

Reimagining English Education through Translanguaging: A Critical Case Study of an EFL Classroom in Senegal. *Ndrao Faye, University of Nebraska - Lincoln*

Encountering Uncertainty: Reimagining Teacher Education. *Andrea Lira, Universidad de Magallanes*

Chair: *Giovanni E. Whyte, University of North Dakota*

77.069-10. Youth Leadership and Action (Table 10).

SIG-Environmental Education; Roundtable Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Competing Narratives of Environmental Advocacy Across Two Early Elementary Classrooms. *Ryan E. Hughes, University of North Carolina - Greensboro; Jay M. Shuttleworth, City University of New York, Queens College*

"If Not Me, Then Who?": On the Reimagination of Transformative Environmental Education through Youth Participatory Action Research. *Emmeline Hoogland, Simon Fraser University; Serena Yan-Zhi Chin, University of British Columbia; Engida Hailye Gebre, Simon Fraser University*

Towards a 'reparative climate education': lessons from a youth climate fellowship program. *Preeti Nayak, University of Toronto*

Chair: *Krisanna L. Machtmes, Ohio University*

Discussant: *Sophie Rebecca Korn Gallagher, Los Angeles County*

Office of Education

77.070. AERA Roundtable Session Saturday 1:45 pm - Gold 1;
Roundtable Session

77.070-1. Roundtable Session 7: Student Learning and Development in College and Beyond (Table 1). Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

For Better or Worse: Multidirectional Social Comparisons in Predicting Undergraduate Students' Learning Motivation and Engagement. *Yuejia Gao, East China Normal University; Yi Jiang, East China Normal University*

From Needs to Engagement: Supporting Special Enrollment Students through a College Transition Program in China. *Ruitian Lin, Shanghai Jiao Tong University; Xin Gao, Shanghai Jiao Tong University; Yuerong Tong, Shanghai Jiao Tong University; Tingting Zhang, Shanghai Jiao Tong University; Shuo Feng, Shanghai Jiao Tong University; Shuai Wang, Shanghai Jiao Tong University*

Learning to Labor: How Internships Reproduce the Culture of Elite Chinese College Students. *Xinyue Zhou, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; qian xiao peng, East China Normal University; Hui Dong, East China Normal University*

Mapping Extracurricular Time Use among High-Achieving College Students: A Cluster-Based Typology. *Yi Wang, Xiamen University*

77.070-2. Roundtable 3 (Table 2). Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Women in Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM): A Comparative Analysis of Degree Attainment. *JoHyun Kim, Texas A&M University; Dohyun Kim, Texas A&M University; Hee Jung Gong, University of Alabama; Seong Ji Jeong, Pennsylvania State University*

How Much Have Times Changed? Mental Health Predicting College Success Before, During, and "After" COVID-19. *Sora Moon, University of Iowa; Nicholas A. Bowman, University of Iowa*

Assessing Undergraduate Success During COVID 19: A Multi Indicator, Equity Minded Institutional Analysis. *Ashley Burle, Saint Louis University*

Chair: *Lina Safa, Pepperdine University*

77.070-3. Institutional Responsibilities for Teaching, Learning, and Community Engagement (Table 3). Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Reimagining Teaching and Learning Centers: A Mixed-Methods Study of Practices in Turkish Higher Education. *Bengi Birgili Karabulut, MEF University; Ömer Demir, Hakkari University*

A Critical Examination of Hong Kong Universities' Efforts in Transforming Teaching and Learning for Sustainability. *Weiyan Xiong, Education University of Hong Kong; Yabing Liu, Education University of Hong Kong*

Colleges and universities as place-makers: Understanding the "community" in higher education-community engagement. *Sondra Nicole Barringer, Southern Methodist University; Brianna R. Freshwater, Southern Methodist University*

Chair: *Jeff Ching-Fan Lai, University of Iowa*

77.070-4. Who Governs Education? Power, Law, and Institutional Change Across Systems (Table 4). Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Stakeholder Conceptualization of Students' Participation Units within Colleges of Education in Brong and Ashanti Regions of Ghana. *Ophelia Affreh, University of Cape Coast*
"It's the Mayor's Show": Public Engagement in Education Policy in Washington, D.C. *Alisha Butler, Wesleyan University; Kristin Sinclair, Georgetown University; Kaden Miller, Wesleyan University*

Arizona's Proposition 203: A Language Critical Race Theory Analysis of Affective Governance in Educational Policy. *Betul Ozel, University of Arizona*

Where are the Kids? Mahmoud v. Taylor and the Constitutional Rewriting of Public Education. *Christopher D. Thomas, University of Florida*

Scrutinizing "industry-education integration" policies in China's higher education: A post-structural analysis. *Tengteng Zhuang, Beijing Normal University*

Chair: *Shantel Palacio, University of New Hampshire*

77.070-5. Mixed Methods Approaches to Identifying Policy Solutions to Absenteeism (Table 5). Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Linking Student Wellbeing and Chronic Absenteeism: Evidence from Georgia. *Jerome Graham, Michigan State University; Su Yon Choi, Michigan State University; Richard O. Welsh, Vanderbilt University; Daphne M. Penn, Vanderbilt University; Kathryn Enriquez, Vanderbilt University*

Planning to deliver: A mixed-methods study of what

contributes to absenteeism intervention delivery. *Kayla Fike, Vanderbilt University; Changhee Lee, Vanderbilt University; Hannah Morris, Vanderbilt University; Eli Rolfes, Vanderbilt University; Ryan Anthony La Barrie, Vanderbilt University; David K. Diehl, Vanderbilt University; Carol L. Brown, Metro Nashville Board of Education*

Reverse Engineering Success in Reducing Absenteeism: Considerations and Challenges for Identifying and Learning from Outliers. *Richard O. Welsh, Vanderbilt University; Kathryn Enriquez, Vanderbilt University; Jerome Graham, Michigan State University; Su Yon Choi, Michigan State University*

Chair: *Tom Shields, University of Richmond*

77.070-6. Policy in Human Hands: Agency, Leadership, and the People Who Make Policy Work (Table 6). Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Roundtable Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Analyzing Policy Learning from Research and Practice: A Qualitative Document Analysis of Career Support for Universities. *chan soo moon, Kukje University of Arts; Hyena Lee, Korea Employment Information Service; jinsol Lee, Korea Research Institute for Vocational Education and Training*

How Education Policy-based Discourse Relates to Kindergarten Teacher Agency? A Post-structural Analysis. *Chrysa Pui Chi Keung, Education University of Hong Kong; Yinuo Wang, The Education University of Hong Kong*

Leading from the Middle: The Evolving Role of School Superintendents in the Context of Networked Governance. *Livia A.J. Jesacher-Roessler, Friedrich-Alexander-University Erlangen-Nuremberg; Katharina Nessler, University of Erlangen - Nuremberg; Nina Bremm, Friedrich-Alexander University Erlangen-Nuremberg*

Reimagining School Leaders for a Post-Plyler World: Refuge and Resources for Undocumented Students. *Liliana E. Castrellon, San José State University; Marina López, University of California - Los Angeles; Alonso R. Reyna Rivarola, Salt Lake Community College; Érica Fernández, Miami University (OH); Gerardo R. López, Michigan State University*

Chair: *Liliana E. Castrellon, San José State University*

77.070-7. Language, Multilingualism, and Linguistic Equity (Table 7). SIG-Early Education and Child Development; Roundtable Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Multilingualism and Teacher-Child Linguistic Congruence as Predictors of Young Children's Emotional Competence. *Craig S. Bailey, Yale University; Qiaoyu Zhou, Yale Child*

Study Center; Claire Mauney, Byram Hills High School
Dual Language Abilities and Socioemotional Development for Spanish-English Dual Language Learners in Head Start. *Ye Shen, Johns Hopkins University; Rui Wang, Mathematica*
Associations between Caregivers' Open- and Closed-ended Questions and Toddlers' Language Skills in Senegal. *Yatma Diop, University of Vermont; Lori Skibbe, Michigan State University*

Forging New Paths by Building on Biographies: Fostering Early Childhood Teacher Readiness for Bi/Multilingual Learners. *Melissa Ann Holmes, Kansas State University; Socorro Herrera, Kansas State University*

A Qualitative Investigation of Digital Home Literacy Environment Among Chinese English Learners. *Jiaqi Guo, The Education University of Hong Kong; Siu Sze Yeung, The Education University of Hong Kong*

Chair: *Ye Shen, Johns Hopkins University*

77.070-8. Posthuman Reimaginings of Teaching and Teacher Education (Table 8). SIG-Critical Posthuman and Postfoundational Studies in Education; Roundtable Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

How Special Education Teacher Candidates Understand Neurodiversity in Films: An Examination of Students' Papers. *Shalinie Sarju, SUNY Old Westbury*

Latent becoming: Pre-service teachers learning to teach engineering in elementary and middle grades. *Max Vazquez Dominguez, University of North Georgia; Lourdes Cardozo-Gaibisso, Mississippi State University*

Playing within the Breaking Points: Schizoanalysis and Social Studies Teaching. *Peter M Nelson, University of British Columbia; Jahnek Rai, Lord Tweedsmuir Secondary School*

Reconceptualizing Teacher Agency: Immanent Events and Posthuman Futures. *Mark Hardman, Institute of Education - London*

Vision of Knowledge and Affective Facts: College Teaching in US State Higher Education Legislation. *Anastasia Y. Goodwin, Vanderbilt University*

Chair: *Edith P. Middleton, Teachers College, Columbia University*

77.071. AERA Roundtable Session Saturday 1:45 pm - Gold 2; Roundtable Session

77.071-1. Advancing the Measurement of Teaching: Innovations in Observation and Evaluation (Table 1). SIG-Classroom Observation; Roundtable Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Designing a Low-Inference Measure to Capture High-Quality Language and Literacy Instruction in Early Childhood. *Paola Andrea Guerrero-Rosada, University of California -*

Irvine; Inez Montserrat Medina Caro, University of California - Irvine; Tomoko Wakabayashi, Oakland University; Melissa A. Bishop, Oakland University

Revising Teacher Evaluation: A Latent Variable Analysis of Marzano Teacher Effectiveness and School Achievement. Lindsey Devers Basileo, *Instructional Empowerment*; Merewyn E. Lyons, *Instructional Empowerment*; Michael David Toth, *Instructional Empowerment*; Robert Marzano, *Marzano Evaluation Center*; Lorah Neville, *The Marzano Evaluation Center*

Virtual Observation of Small-Group Reading Instruction: Reliability and Validity of a Scalable Measure. Mary Bratsch-Hines, *University of Florida*; Yihua Hong, *RTI International*; Julianna Banks, *University of Florida*; Rui Xu, *University of Florida*; Heather H Aiken, *University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*; Robin Wisniewski, *RTI International*

77.071-2. Civic Education, Technology and AI (Table 2). SIG-Democratic Citizenship in Education; Roundtable Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

AI for Civic and Social Inquiry: Examining Student Understanding and Use. Kelsey Leigh Stokes, *Baylor University*; Kevin R. Magill, *Baylor University*; Millicent Weber, *Baylor University*; Maggie Bryant, *Baylor University*

Students Discussing Civic Issues Online with Politically Diverse Peers: Fostering Open-Minded Political Engagement. Brett L. M. Levy, *University at Albany - SUNY*; Alina Lewis, *University at Albany - SUNY*; Christopher Wegemer, *University of California - Los Angeles*

Teacher Subjectivity Toward AI in Addressing Controversial Issues for Civic Education. Hyelin Kim, *University of Georgia*

77.071-3. Inclusive and Equitable Rural Education: Care, Community, and Student Well-Being (Table 3). SIG-Rural Education; Roundtable Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Creating Spaces for LGBTQ+ Belongingness in Rural Areas: A Study of Safe Spaces and People. Karen Schreder, *California State University - Chico*; Waylon C Miller, *California State University - Chico*; Veronica Ulloa, *California State University - Chico*

How Does Marital Conflict Influence Chinese rural Students' Mental Health? *guan di*, *Beijing Normal University*

Inclusive Design for Emancipatory and Liberatory Education (IDEAL): Foundations and Implementation in Rural Elementary Schools. Robert White, *ECSU*

The impact of an emergent bilingual professional development experience on teachers in rural districts. Marisol Diaz,

California State Polytechnic University - Pomona; Chrissy J Cross, *Stephen F. Austin State University*; Heather K. Olson Beal, *Stephen F. Austin State University*

They're blossoming: Cultivating care in a rural kindergarten classroom. Stephanie Oudghiri Scherer, *Purdue University*
Chair: Ingrid A. Nelson, *Bowdoin College*

77.071-4. Designing Learning for All: UDL and Inclusive Curriculum (Table 4). SIG-Special and Inclusive Education Research; Roundtable Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

From Training to Teaching: The Impact of UDL Faculty Professional Development on Student Perceptions. Christopher D. Hromalik, *SUNY Oswego*; Elnara Mammadova, *Purdue University*

Learning through Composite Narratives: Inclusive Teaching Experiences for Teacher Education Programs. Emilee A Baker, *University of Minnesota*; Rebekah Wallis, *Syracuse University*; Christine Elaine Ashby, *Syracuse University*

UDL Takes a Village: University Faculty Reflections on Accountability and Infrastructure. Amy Accardo, *Rowan University*; Brie Morettini, *Rowan University*; Erin B. Hedges, *Rowan University*

Chair: Jackieelyn Domingo Ruiz, *New York University*

77.071-5. Fostering Social-Emotional Competence and Wellbeing (Table 5). SIG-Special and Inclusive Education Research; Roundtable Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

A Review of the Education and Stigmatization of Students with Emotional and Behavioral Disorders. Karly Conroy, *University of Texas at Austin*

Methodological Issues in Research on Mental Health and Wellbeing of Parents of Children with Developmental Disabilities: A Literature Review. Jing Su, *University of California - Santa Barbara*

Exploring the Prevalence of Co-occurring Externalizing and Internalizing Problems in Students with Learning Disabilities. Nayoung Yoon, *University of Texas at Austin*

Chair: Sarah A Caroleo, *Brown University*

77.071-6. Teacher Research as an Approach to Contribute to the Knowledge Base (Table 6). SIG-Teacher as Researcher; Roundtable Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Authentic Spaces for Teacher Collaborative Inquiry: Examining Peer Partners Through an Improvement Science Lens. Huy Quoc Chung, *University of California - Irvine*; Michael

Hebert, University of California - Irvine; Elizabeth Harrington, University of California, Irvine-Writing Project; Emily McCourtney, University of California, Irvine-Writing Project; Melissa Galvan, University of California, Irvine-Writing Project

Echoes in the Code: A Teacher-Researcher's Reckoning with Black Archives and AI Texts. *Abdul-Qadir D. Islam, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Integrating Teachers' Cultures and Children's Inquiry to Develop a Culturally Appropriate Curriculum. *Hyejin Do, San Francisco State University; Mina Kim, San Francisco State University*

"You Should Not Judge, You Should Understand": The Effects and Perceptions of an Empathy Embedded Teacher Inquiry Framework. *Erica J Milor, University of South Florida - Tampa*

Chair: *Kevin Cataldo, Newark Board of Education/Montclair State University*

77.071-7. Skills and Strategies for Teaching History: Approaches and Considerations (Table 7). SIG-Teaching History; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

History Teachers' and Historians' Beliefs about Presentism. *James Miles, University of Alberta; Lindsay S. Gibson, University of British Columbia; Rachel Moylan, University of British Columbia*

History Teachers' Understandings of Rightwing Movements and How to Teach Them. *Rob Martinelle, Boston University; Lightning Jay, Binghamton University - SUNY; Christopher C. Martell, University of Massachusetts - Boston*

Solidarity Dreaming: Participatory Inquiry into Baltimore's Histories and Geographies Toward Black-Im/migrant Futures. *Soo Bin Jang, University of Delaware; Amanda Man, University of Delaware; Keondra A Prier, University of Delaware*

Chair: *Christopher C. Martell, University of Massachusetts - Boston*

77.071-8. Developing an Academic Identity (Table 8). SIG-Faculty Teaching, Evaluation, and Development; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

"I Have Doubts": Examining Imposter Syndrome and Its Relationship to Motivation. *Sharmin Rahman, University of North Dakota; Bijaya Shrestha, University of North Dakota; Nathan C. Hall, Government of Canada; Robert H. Stupnisky, University of North Dakota*

Intrinsic Motivation is Not Enough to Reach Full Professor – A Qualitative Exploration of Mid-Career Faculty. *Margaret L*

Roberts, University of the Pacific

Understanding Faculty Job Satisfaction through Self-Determination Theory: Exploring Direct and Indirect Effects of Perceived Support, Psychological Needs, and Employment Status. *Yi Leaf Zhang, University of Texas - Arlington; John Connolly, University of Texas at Arlington*

Tying the Legs Together: Making the Case for Service to Professional Societies as High Impact Faculty Development. *Jonathan S. Toccoli, University of the Pacific; Robert Bartsch, University of Houston - Clear Lake; Laura Cruz, Pennsylvania State University; Ted Murcray, California Baptist University; Lisa A Lambert Snodgrass, Purdue University*

77.071-9. Advancing Inclusion and Belonging in Doctoral and Postgraduate Education (Table 9). SIG-Graduate and Postdoctoral Education across the Disciplines; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Addressing Translingual Turn and the Knowledge Diaspora Across Disciplines. *Suok Kwon, Stetson University*

Integrating Universal Design for Learning (UDL) in postgraduate education: A mixed-methods study. *Ning Ren, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Gary Lam, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Ronnel B. King, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Anthony MC So, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Vivian WY LEE, The Chinese University of Hong Kong*

Mapping the Invisible Currents: Emotional, Social, and Organizational Influences on First-Generation PhD Career Trajectories. *Jesse McCain, University of Virginia; Charlotte Hayes, Florida State University; Annie M. Wofford, Florida State University; Josipa Roksa, University of Virginia*

Nurturing Scholar-Practitioner Identities: A Case Study of Socialization in a CPED-aligned Ed.D. Program. *Alexios Rosario-Moore, Northern Illinois University; Marissa Bamberger, Northern Illinois University; Daryl Mortensen Dugas, Northern Illinois University*

Well-Being and Belonging: Creating Transformative Graduate Student Learning Environments. *Shelley Price-Williams, University of Northern Iowa*

77.072. AERA Roundtable Session Saturday 1:45 pm - Gold 3; Roundtable Session

77.072-1. Reflection and Transformation: Centering Disabled Students' Perspectives in Shaping the Future of Higher Education (Table 1). SIG-Disability Studies in Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Disabled Voices in Higher Education: A Photovoice Project.
Sylvia Mac, University of San Diego

Exploring disabled students' experiences of learning and perspectives of accessible instruction in postsecondary education. *Emily Tarconish, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Shafagh Hadinezhad, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Logan Hillary Lauren, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Pursuing Inclusivity: Narrating Episodic Disability and Accommodation Access in Higher Education. *Daniela Pucci, University of Toronto; Julia Forgie, University of Toronto*

Students with Mental Health Diagnoses: Experiences with Faculty at Research 1 Universities. *Alyson Thach, Claremont Graduate University*

Chairs: *Claudia Chiang-Frost, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Kavya Sree Mariboyina, Little Priest Tribal College*

77.072-2. Learning to Teach, Teaching to Liberate: Black Teachers and Pedagogical Freedom (Table 2). SIG-Research Focus on Black Education; Roundtable Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Exploring Black Preservice Teacher Identity using a Black Education Studies Curriculum. *Travon Jefferson, Michigan State University*

Learning to Teach, Teaching to Liberate: Black Teachers and the RE-construction of a Liberatory Pedagogy. *E. Anthony Muhammad, Georgia Southern University; Sheena N. Odom, Muscogee County School District; Lastasia Ramsey, Georgia Southern University; Ashley Griffin Gilchrist, Bowie State University*

Straight Outta (but not of) Suburbia: Reflecting & Projecting On Black Teacher & Student Experiences. *Tamra Gertrude Jenkins, University of the Pacific; Andre Tyrece Carter, University of San Francisco*

The Sista Circle Lab Methodology: Building an Humanizing Self-Definition for Black Women Science Teachers. *Alexis Riley, New York University*

Chair: *Shawn S. Savage, University of North Carolina - Wilmington*

77.072-3. Measuring Black Educational Justice: Data, Discipline, and Disparities (Table 3). SIG-Research Focus on Black Education; Roundtable Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Black Education, Racial Inequities, and Exclusionary Discipline: A Qualitative Meta-synthesis of Student Perspectives. *Dina Malala, Texas A&M University; Sarah Lee, Texas A&M University; eboni bailey bonaiti, Texas A&M University; Megan Bishop, Texas A&M University;*

Ekta Ghosh, University of Denver; Stephanie LaShawn Jackson, Texas A&M University

District-Level Variation in Black Students' Academic Improvement. *Darnell Leatherwood, University of Michigan; Faeze Safari, University of Connecticut; Jennifer Aracely Rodriguez, University of Michigan Ann Arbor*

Heterogeneity in Black Student Achievement Across U.S. School Districts. *Darnell Leatherwood, University of Michigan; Faeze Safari, University of Connecticut; Jennifer Aracely Rodriguez, University of Michigan Ann Arbor*

Crisis as Revelation: Black Women Student Affairs Professionals and the Matrix of Domination During COVID-19. *Evangela Q. Oates, University of Minnesota; Kaleb L. Briscoe, University of Oklahoma; LaWanda W. Ward, Pennsylvania State University; Brittany Washington, University of Oklahoma; Morgan Okello, Pennsylvania State University*

Chair: *Lisa Bass, North Carolina State University*

77.072-4. Digital and Multimodal Gendered Explorations (Table 4). SIG-Research on Women and Education; Roundtable Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Women's Solidarity in Neoliberal Institutions through Digital Activism: Reclaiming Voice and Agency in Higher Education. *Gunel Alasgarova, The Ohio State University; Turana Abdullayeva, University of Sheffield*

SOCIO-ECONOMIC STATUS (SES) AND CLIMATE LITERACY AMONG RURAL WOMEN OF GILGIT CITY: A MEDIATING ROLE OF USE OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES (ICTs). *Irfan Nawaz, Ministry of Human Rights, Islamabad; Nazir ullah, Centre of Engineering Research Advancement and Technology (CEERAT); Nisha Irfan, Quaid-e-Azam University, Islamabad*

Gender and Racial Bias in AI-Generated Letters of Recommendation. *Kayla Nunes, University of California - Irvine; Stephanie Reich, University of California - Irvine; Zhenyao Cai, University of California - Irvine; Natalia Pilavian, University of California - Irvine*

77.072-5. The Community Matters: Toward Action-Minded Practice, Using a Photovoice Method, and Through Emotionally Intelligent Action Researchers/Educators (Table 5). SIG-Action Research; Roundtable Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Moving Past "All Deliberate Speed": An Action-Oriented Approach to School Integration Research. *Liz D. Nigro, University of Virginia*

Photovoice Paints a Fuller Picture: Employing an Arts-Based

Photographic Research Method with Black Communities. *Jenay Willis, University of Mississippi; Jaminque L. Adams, University of Georgia*

Teaching With Heart: How Emotionally Intelligent Educators Shape Inclusive Junior High Communities. *Colette Bozek, Knowledgehook*

77.072-6. Navigating Choice and Inequity: Family Agency and Structural Constraints in Education (Table 6). SIG-Charters & School Choice; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Accessing opportunity: Children with disabilities, their families, and Education Savings Accounts. *Georgia Heyward, Virginia Commonwealth University*

Against an Anti-Black Racist Schooling Landscape: Racialized Risk Assessments in Black Families' School Choice. *De'Ja Wood, Vanderbilt University*

Geographic Disparities in Access to Affordable, High-Quality Prekindergarten Across Indiana. *Jiyeon Lee, Ball State University; Jin Lee, University of Louisiana at Lafayette*

Unschooling the System: Learning Pods, Family Choice, and the Rewriting of Educational Futures. *Stacy-Ann Campbell, Louisiana State University; Veysel Altunel, Louisiana State University; Henderson Lewis, Louisiana State University*

Chair: *Chrystal S. Johnson, Purdue University*

77.072-7. Transformation, or Not, in Childhood Education? (Table 7). SIG-Critical Peace Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

AI Meets Peace: Transforming Teacher Training for Early Childhood Education. *Maryam Sadat Sharifian, James Madison University*

Youth Participatory Action Research in Delhi, India. Moving into Possibilities and a Sense of Hopefulness. *Kamiya Kumar, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Reimagining Peace Education in Conflict Zones: A Critical Case Study of Indigenous Peace Education at the Congo Peace School. *Samwel Mnanga Petro, University of Maryland*

77.072-8. Exploring parents' perspectives on school-technology engagement (Table 8). SIG-Family, School, Community Partnerships; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Digital Capital as an Emerging Resource in Parent-School Interactions. *Audrey Addi-Raccah, Tel Aviv University*

Imagining a New Future for Technology: Engaging Parents and

Families in Computer Science Education. *Jean J. Ryoo, University of California - Los Angeles; Michelle Choi, University of California - Los Angeles; Julie Flapan, University of California - Los Angeles; Sharisa Chan, University of California - Los Angeles*

Beyond behavior management: Exploring the role of ClassDojo in parent-teacher relationships. *Vincent Cho, Boston College; Sofia Duenas, University of Notre Dame; Sergio David Barragan, Boston College*

Examining Mothers' Perspectives on Children's Digital At-Home and In-School Learning. *Alyssa R. Gonzalez-Dehass, Florida Atlantic University; Jacqueline Lynch, Florida International University; Patricia Pulido Willems, Florida Atlantic University*

Meta-Analysis of the Associations between Digital Parenting and Children's Positive Digital Well-being Outcomes. *Naiqi Xu, The University of Hong Kong; Cheng Yong Tan, University of Hong Kong; Mengyi Liang, The University of Hong Kong*

Chair: *Anastasia L. Betts, Learnology Labs*

77.072-9. Home and schools: Promoting language and literacy development (Table 9). SIG-Family, School, Community Partnerships; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Empowering Parents to Support Kindergarteners' English Language Development. *Ghadah Al Murshidi, UAE University; Ahmed Al Zaabi, Dubai Police; Zayed Al Zaabi, Al Itihad Private School Jumairah*

Collaborative Literacy Support for Multilingual Caregivers: A Stakeholder-Informed Approach. *Mihaela Gazioglu, Westfield State University; Lindsey W. Rowe, Clemson University; Emily S. Howell, Clemson University; Nicole Ferguson-Sams, Clemson University; Alexis Lawton, Clemson University*

Exploring, Engaging, Empowering: A Mixed-Methods Study Informing a Family and Community-Based Early Literacy Plan. *Rebekah C. Louis, Stonehill College; Amy Leshinsky, Curry College*

Teachers' Evolving Understanding of Home Literacy Practices: A Case Study of an After-School Family Literacy Program. *Jennifer Bryson, Boston University*

Home-School Partnerships and Supporting Literacy Learning at Home. *Laura Teichert, Western Michigan University; Kristen Janecko, Western Michigan University; Blakeley Kiser, Western Michigan University; Lauren Remington, Western Michigan University*

Chair: *Jenny Tuten, Hunter College - CUNY*

77.073. AERA Roundtable Session Saturday 1:45 pm - Gold 4;
Roundtable Session

77.073-1. Multimodal Literacies: Visual, Digital, and Oral Perspectives (Table 1). Division C - Learning and Instruction; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Automated Analysis of Teacher-Child Language Interactions in Pre-K Classrooms. *Elizabeth Burke Hadley, University of South Florida - Tampa; John Hansen, University of Texas - Dallas; Jiamin Xie, University of Texas - Dallas; Eunsook Kim, University of South Florida; Dwight Irvin, University of Florida; Sara A. Smith, University of Florida*

Enhancing Receptive and Expressive Language Skills through the Phonomimic Method in Kindergarten. *Renata Kiss, University of Szeged; Dora Mokri, University of Szeged; Margit Fazekasné Fenyvesi, Károli Gáspár University of the Reformed Church*

Oral Language and Reading Development: Insights from a Systematic Replication Across Diverse Contexts. *Holland Kowalkowski, University of Texas at Austin; Dora Diaz, University of Texas at Austin; Ling Chen, University of Massachusetts - Amherst; Yixian Huang, University of Texas at Austin; Doris Luft Baker, University of Texas at Austin; Cara R. Richards, California State University - Long Beach; Vivian Wong, University of Virginia; Emily J. Solari, University of Virginia*

Putting Words to Pictures: Defining, Classifying, and Exemplifying the Static Visuals Used in Multimodal Research. *Jannah Fuseinig, University of Maryland; Patricia A. Alexander, University of Maryland*

Fostering a Co-constructed Multimodal Learning Space Through Digital Multimodal Compositions in Elementary Multilingual Classrooms. *Hongye Zeng, University of Maryland; Hannah Park, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Chair: *Rachel Besharat Mann, Wesleyan University*

77.073-2. Framing Effort, Building Efficacy: Motivational Insights Across Contexts (Table 2). Division C - Learning and Instruction; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Task-Dependent Effects of Effort Framing on Perceived Effort, Study Time, and Learning Outcomes. *Yiting Hao, Shenzhen University; Lars-Erik Malmberg, University of Oxford; Gabriel J. Stylianides, University of Oxford*

Motivational Orientation and Concept Mapping Formats: Effects on Retention and Transfer in Chemistry Learning. *Blessing Akinrotimi, Washington State University; Oluwajemi J. Sunday, Washington State University; Yetunde Morenike Adaramola, Washington State University*

The Hidden Price of Achievement: Linking Cost Perceptions to Mindset, Belonging, and Performance. *Rylan Deer, The Ohio State University; Shirley L. Yu, The Ohio State*

University; Kimiko Ching, The Ohio State University; Andrew Holmes Perry, The Ohio State University; Wonjoon Cha, The Ohio State University

Impact of Prompt Types on Task-Specific Self-Efficacy and Self-Evaluation in Problem Posing. *Ibrahim Burak Olmez, University of Delaware; Stephen Hwang, University of Delaware; Jinfa Cai, University of Delaware*

“Help-Seeking 2.0”: Exploring GenAI Help-Seeking Among STEM Undergraduates Using an Expectancy-Value-Cost Framework. *Zohreh Fathi, Texas State University; Pedram Zarei, Texas State University; Pegah Peimani, Texas State University; IMANEH SOLEIMANI, Texas State University; Zachary Baquet, University of Houston; Stephen Oluwaseyi Maku, Texas State University; Carlton J. Fong, Texas State University*

Chair: *Elise C. Allen, University of Northern Colorado*

77.073-3. AI, Writing, and Learner Agency in Educational Contexts (Table 3). Division C - Learning and Instruction; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Design-Based Research to Enhance Collaboration between Learners and AI in a Middle School Writing Class. *Hyeoun Kim, Seoul National University; Young Hoan Cho, Seoul National University; Minju Kang, Seoul National University; Yeono Son, Seoul National University*

Exploring changing profiles of students’ adoption and diffusion of using ChatGPT for learning: A latent transitional analysis. *Yuhan Xiong, Education University of Hong Kong; Norman B. Mendoza, The Education University of Hong Kong; Xiaoying Li, ELCHK Lutheran Academy; Zi Yan, The Education University of Hong Kong*

From Curiosity to Confidence: How Wearable VR and Chatbots Support Older Learners in Anti-Phishing Education. *Jerry Chih-Yuan Sun, National Yang Ming Chiao Tung University; Yu-Ching Chiu, National Yang Ming Chiao Tung University; Aaron Hagedorn, University of Southern California; Li-An Li, National Yang Ming Chiao Tung University*

Silent, Self-Directed Learning: Navigating Anxiety, Integrity, and Taboo in AI Use. *Merih Ugurel Kamisli, TED University*

The Effects of Generative AI on Undergraduate Writing. *Maryam Eslami, University of California - Irvine; Penelope Collins, University of California - Irvine*

Chair: *Yun Dai, Chinese University of Hong Kong*

77.073-4. Feedback and Assessment in Digital Learning Environments (Table 4). Division C - Learning and Instruction; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

A Systematic Review of K-12 Computational Thinking Assessment in Digital Learning Environments. *Maryam Babae, University of Florida; Seyedahmad Rahimi, University of Florida*

Impact of Affective Features of Feedback Providers on Multimedia Learning: An Eye-Tracking Study. *Fangzheng Zhao, Nanjing Normal University; Richard E. Mayer, University of California - Santa Barbara*

Introducing Variability into Multiple-Choice Exercises: A Desirable Difficulty to Enhance Technology-Based Practice Testing. *Marc Philipp Janson, Karlsruhe University of Education; Paula Schmelzer, University of Mannheim; Samuel Wissel, University of Mannheim; Benedict C.O.F. Fehringer, University of Mannheim; Stefan Munzer, University of Mannheim*

More is not always better: Exploring the relationship between digital inquiry-based learning and academic performance and the moderating role of feedback. *Qinhui Huang, Beijing Normal University; Luyang Guo, University of Macau*

Rethinking Feedback: Student Perceptions of Instructor-Created and AI-Generated Instant Feedback in Higher Education Courses. *Xiaoying Zheng, Indiana University; Gamze Ozogul, Indiana University - Bloomington; Seung Lee, North Carolina State University; Wookhee Min, North Carolina State University; Dan Carpenter, North Carolina State University; Jordan Esiason, North Carolina State University; James C. Lester, North Carolina State University*

Chair: *Feral Ogan-Bekiroglu, Marmara University*

77.073-5. Navigating Borders: Learning, Equity, and Youth Agency in Transnational Contexts (Table 5). SIG-

Cultural-Historical Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Beyond Borders: The Reach of Authoritarianism in the Academic Lives of Russian Students Abroad. *Anastasia Lavrenyuk, University of Maryland*

Beyond Compliance: Systemic Contradictions in Implementing Equity Policy for Emergent Bilingual Learners in the Borderlands. *Sumin Lim, Hunter College; Dosun Ko, Santa Clara University; Yehyang Lee, Syracuse University*

ECO-Young: Ecologies Of Learning For Climate Transformations In The Lives Of Brazilian And Senegalese Young People. *Monica Lemos, Colégio Rio Branco; Antti J. Rajala, University of Eastern Finland; Eleonora Lundell, University of Neuchatel*

Learning as moving through immigrating, settling, and documenting stories: Imagining possibilities for Canadian newcomer youth. *Natacha Monestel-Mora, University of British Columbia; Jennifer A. Vadeboncoeur, University of British Columbia*

Chair: *Tamara Handy, Teachers College, Columbia University*

77.073-6. Designing Immersive Learning Environment (Table 6). SIG-Instructional Technology; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Co-Designing Metadata for Discoverability: Supporting K-12 Teachers' Access to Educational Resources. *Yifan Zhang, Beijing Normal University; Lori Pollock, University of Delaware; Chrystalla Mouza, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Exploring the Impact of VR Visual Design on Students' Physiological Arousal in Public Speaking Tasks. *Gege Li, Central China Normal University; Heng Luo, Central China Normal University*

One Hint Doesn't Fit All: Learner Characteristics and Hint Design in Digital Learning Games. *Zeinab Mokhtari, Dresden University of Technology; Mahboobeh Mehrvarz, Carnegie Mellon University; Bruce McLaren, Carnegie Mellon University; Seyedahmad Rahimi, University of Florida; Esmá Nur Kahveci, University of Massachusetts - Dartmouth; Samaneh Abdoli, Farhangian University*

Peer Review in Classroom Design Virtual Reality: Leveraging Diverse Perspectives for Connection and Competency-Building. *Kelly Davis, University of Houston; Susie Gronseth, University of Houston; Tony Liao, University of Houston; Justin T. Burris, University of Houston; Sammy Tawakkol, University of Houston; Leslie A. Coward, University of Houston*

Chair: *Lei Wang, Auburn University - Montgomery*

77.073-7. Intervention Innovations: Leveraging and Learning From Motivational Processes (Table 7). SIG-Motivation in Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Enhancing College Transitions Through a Synergistic Mindset Intervention. *Sarah Leckey, University of California - Davis; Cameron Hecht, University of Rochester; Heather Rose, University of California - Davis; Jacob Hibel, University of California - Davis; Yushan Zhao, University of California - Davis; Karla Santana Valenton, University of California - Davis; Evelyn Mandujano, University of California - Davis; Susan Ebeler, University of California - Davis; Kali Trzesniewski, University of California - Davis*

Failing to improve: investigating when a growth mindset backfires. *Makita White, Washington State University; Elizabeth A. Canning, Washington State University*

Motivating Open-Mindedness and Intellectual Humility in Adolescence. *Tenelle Porter, Rowan University; Jon M. Valant, Brookings; Daniel Newark, HEC Paris*

Practice Makes Proficient: A Randomized Controlled Trial of Growth-Based Assessments in Introductory Calculus

Courses. *Michelle K Francis, University of Virginia; Delaram A. Totonchi, University of Virginia; Joshua Davis, University of Virginia; Daneil James, University of Virginia; Jim Rolf, University of Virginia; Chris S. Hulleman, University of Virginia; Yoi Tibbets*

Chair: *Yeo-eun Kim, Sungkyunkwan University*

77.073-8. From Mentorship to Classroom Innovation:

Supporting Teachers' Assessment Literacy (Table 8).

SIG-Classroom Assessment; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Examining Assessment Literacy Development Through
Practicum-Based Mentorship: A Systematic Review.

*Oluyemisi Ajoke Oloniyo, Washington State University;
Chad M. Gotch, Washington State University*

Assessment Innovation: Advancing an Empirically-Informed
Theory of Teacher-Led Assessment Change. *Christopher
DeLuca, Queen's University - Kingston; Andrew Coombs,
Memorial University of Newfoundland; Danielle LaPointe-
McEwan, Queen's University - Kingston; Nathan H. Rickey,
Queen's University - Kingston; Brinanne Chafe, Memorial
University of Newfoundland*

The Effect of an Assessment Training Video on Music
Educators' Rating Accuracy of Singing Performance.
*Kathleen Arrasmith, University of South Carolina; Xiaobo
Wei, University of South Carolina; Ashlee A. Lewis,
University of South Carolina*

Situative Assessment in Online and Open Learning: Transfer,
Equity, and Design Principles. *Daniel T. Hickey, Indiana
University; Tripp Harris, University of South Carolina*

Chair: *Serafina Pastore, University of Bari*

**77.073-9. Teachers and teacher agency across PBL learning
environments (Table 9).** SIG-Problem-Based and Project-
Based Learning; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Empowering STEM Teachers to Design Driving Question for
Project-Based Learning through Digital Scaffolding. *jin
shen, Beijing Normal University; dingyue weng, Beijing
Normal University; Yenny Mo, North Central Texas College;
Peter Chan, Brigham Young University - Hawaii; rui wei,
Beijing Normal University*

Localized Culturally Responsive Mathematics Education
Project-Based Learning Promotes Sustainable Development.
*Dantong Li, Universiti Teknologi Malaysia; Sharifah
Osman, Universiti Teknologi Malaysia; Najua Syuhada
Ahmad Alhassora, Universiti Teknologi Malaysia; Jeya
Amantha Kumar, Michigan State University; Xianming
Huang, East China Normal University*

Navigating Constraints: Teacher Agency in Project-Based

Learning in Chinese High Schools. *Wenmin Zhao,
University of Saint Joseph; Run Wen, Xi'an Jiaotong-
Liverpool University; Rong Wang, Xi'an Jiaotong-Liverpool
University; Mingyu Liu, Suzhou Vocational Health College*
Near-Peer Development of Culturally Relevant, Problem-Based
Science Units. *Stephanie Purington, Marist College;
Christine McGrail, University of North Dakota; Alicia C.
Gonzales, Michigan Technological University*

**77.073-10. RT3: Imputation Strategies and Synthesis/Meta-
Analytic Designs with Mediation Effects or Complex
Structures (Table 10).** Division D - Measurement and
Research Methodologies; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Synthesis of Single-Case Design Mediation Effects using Two-
Stage Multilevel Modeling. *Mariola Moeyaert, University at
Albany - SUNY; Milica Miocevic, McGill University;
Matthew Valente, University of South Florida; Yaosheng
Lou, University at Albany - SUNY*

A Comparison of Approaches for Handling Within-Study
Dependency in Correlations for Meta-Analytic Structural
Equation Modeling. *Sunyoung Park, California Lutheran
University; Tasha Beretvas, University of Texas at Austin*

A Comparison of Methods for Assessing Publication Bias in
Mixed-Effects Meta-Regression Models. *Man Chen,
University of Texas at Austin*

Missing Data Imputation Using Machine Learning: A
Comparative Study with Traditional Mean Imputation.
Yuchen Wang; Zhushan Mandy Li, Boston College

Handling Missing Outcomes in Propensity Score: Comparing
Multiple Imputation and Multiple Imputation-then-Deletion.
*Xinchang Zhou, University of Illinois at Urbana-
Champaign; Yan Xia, University of Illinois at Urbana-
Champaign*

Chair: *Ann A. O'Connell, Rutgers University*

Division and SIG Posters

77.074. AERA Poster Session Saturday 1:45 pm; Poster Session

**77.074-1. Learning in Context: Cognitive, Motivational, and
Technological Pathways Across Diverse Educational
Landscapes.** Division C - Learning and Instruction; Poster
Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall -
Exhibit Hall A; 1:45-3:15pm

Posters:

1. AI for Enhancing Spatial Thinking in South African Urban
Planning Education (Poster 1). *Desiree Nosipho Cele,
University at Buffalo - SUNY; Blessed Aspinas Mhungu,
University at Buffalo - SUNY*

2. Navigating the International Baccalaureate Journey: Challenges and Opportunities Perceived by High School Students and Alumni (Poster 2). *Xiao-Yin Chen, University of Tennessee; Kai Zhuang Shum, University of Tennessee; Chloe Muller, University of Tennessee; Amber Rosamond, University of Tennessee; Sophie Kronenberger, University of Tennessee; Madina Kholnazarova, University of Tennessee*
 3. Testing a Sequenced Values Reflection Intervention Promoting Quantitative Reasoning Skills and Self-Efficacy Beliefs (Poster 3). *Megan Hut, West Virginia University; D. Jake Follmer, West Virginia University*
 4. The Role of Executive Functions in Reading Development: A Longitudinal Multilevel Modeling Approach (Poster 4). *Jieun Park, Middle Tennessee State University; Amy Elleman, Middle Tennessee State University; Yucheng Cao, Middle Tennessee State University*
 5. Where the Rocks Grow: Using photovoice and nature journaling to investigate student experiences in study-abroad (Poster 5). *Kelly Feille, University of Oklahoma; Cian Brown, University of Oklahoma*
 6. Adaptive Reactions to Errors in Elementary School Students: Multimodal Assessment and Effects on Knowledge Acquisition (Poster 6). *Markus Dresel, University of Augsburg; Jana Spear, University of Augsburg; Cara Enste, University of Augsburg; Donna Bryce, University of Augsburg; Robert Grassinger, Pädagogische Hochschule Weingarten; Amadeus Jonathan Pickal, University of Augsburg*
 7. A Video-Based Category System for Identifying Adaptive Teaching Interactions in Elementary Mathematics (Poster 7). *Anne-Kathrin Butchereyt, Bergische University St Wuppertal; Claudia Kastens, University of Wuppertal*
 8. Eye Tracking and Stimulated Recall Evidence of Young Readers' Metacognitive Processes in Science Picture Book Reading (Poster 8). *Zhujun Jiang, Shanghai Jiao Tong University; Tairui Song, East China Normal University; JIAYAN TEY, Shanghai Jiao Tong University; Feng-Kuang Chiang, Shanghai Jiao Tong University*
 9. Injecting utility value in a microbiology class for undergraduate nursing students (Poster 9). *Vanessa Zhang, The Ohio State University; Rylan Deer, The Ohio State University; Huy Nguyen, The Ohio State University; Shirley L. Yu, The Ohio State University; Andrew Holmes Perry, The Ohio State University; Wonjoon Cha, The Ohio State University; Arianna Henning, The Ohio State University; Kimiko Ching, The Ohio State University; Michelle R. Richard, The Ohio State University; Madhura Pradhan, The Ohio State University*
 10. Promotion and Prevention Motivation as Predictors of Students' Study Strategies in Math and Social Science (Poster 10). *Vishal Easwar, Boston College; Cristina D. Zepeda, Vanderbilt University; Meghan Coughlan, Boston College; David B. Miele, Boston College*
 11. Students, Colleagues, and Principals as Contexts Shaping Teacher Self-Efficacy, Instruction, and Job Satisfaction (Poster 11). *Jenny Chaehyun Park, Korea University - Brain and Motivation Research Institute; Suyeon Gena Kim, Korea University - Brain and Motivation Research Institute; Jiwon Kim, Korea University - Brain and Motivation Research Institute; Patricia A. Alexander, University of Maryland; Mimi Bong, Korea University*
 12. Unfolding Effort in Read-Aloud Contexts: Timing Analysis Across Thinking Aloud and Non-Verbalized Reading (Poster 12). *Gal Kaldes, Georgia State University; Elizabeth Tighe, Georgia State University; Joseph Magliano, Georgia State University*
 13. What Affects How Pre-service and In-service Teachers Rate Elementary Students' Creativity?: Demographic and Psychological Interactions (Poster 13). *Sofia Kagan, University of Georgia; Denis Dumas, University of Georgia*
 14. Triangulating Self-Reported Motivation, Self-Regulated Learning via Log-File Data, and Formative Assessments in Introductory Statistics (Poster 14). *Sierra Outerbridge, University of Central Florida; Claudia C. Sutter, CourseKata; Michelle Taub, University of Central Florida*
- 77.074-2. Computer Science Education approaches and techniques in context.** Division C - Learning and Instruction; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 1:45-3:15pm
- Posters:
15. Connecting Classroom Climate to Career Choice in Computer Science for CLD Students with Disabilities (Poster 15). *Iggy V. Monsalve, Florida International University*
 16. Cascading Peer Mentoring in High School, Middle School, and Elementary School Computer Science Classrooms (Poster 16). *Elena Novak, Kent State University; Jason D. Schenker, Kent State University; Gözde McLaughlin, Kent State University; Sima Ahmadi, Kent State University; Yibei Guo, Kent State University; Rui Liu, Kent State University; Lisa A. Borgerding, Kent State University*
 17. Beyond Access and Opportunity in CS: Developing Measures of Culturally Responsive-Sustaining Education Implementation in CS Courses (Poster 17). *Alexandra Adair, The College Board; Cheri Fancsali, Research Alliance for New York City Schools; Kathryn Hill, New York University*
 18. Modeling Science and Shaping Attitudes: Physical Computational Model and Mentorship in STEM+C Learning (Poster 18). *Jiajia Du, Texas A&M University; Ting Liu, Texas A&M University; Tanush Yarram, Texas A&M University; Kirti Sagar Gadde, Texas A&M University; Rebecca Ward, Texas A&M University; Rebecca Jean Schlegel, Texas A&M University*
 19. Analyzing High School Students' Code Comprehension and Strategies Using SOLO Taxonomy and Large Language Models (Poster 19). *Shan Zhang, University of Florida; Priyadharshini Ganapathy Prasad, University of Florida;*

Toni Earle-Randell, University of Florida; Zifeng Liu, University of Florida; Yang Shi, Utah State University; Suma Bhat, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Maya Israel, University of Florida

20. Unpacking the Psychometric Properties of Computational Thinking Measure (Poster 20). *Shaf Ahmed, Utah State University; David F. Feldon, Utah State University*
21. Teaching Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning to Non-Major Students at University: A Scoping Review (Poster 21). *Oguz Koklu, Bogazici University; Muhammet Şahal, Yildiz Technical University; Merve Dede, Istanbul Beykent University*

77.074-3. Understanding Teacher Learning and Practice in Science Education. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Poster Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 1:45-3:15pm

Posters:

22. Characterizing In-the-moment Scaffolding in Supporting Students' Models Interlocking During Phenomenon-Driven Science Instruction (Poster 22). *Idris Solola, Utah State University; Mimi M. Recker, Utah State University; Quentin Biddy, University of Colorado - Boulder*
23. Exploring More Possibilities of Scientific Inquiry in Classrooms: Teachers' Practical Wisdom in Inquiry-based Teaching (Poster 23). *Jiaxin Tang, University of Utah*
24. Leveraging Learning Progressions to Support Teacher Adaptation and Student 3D Learning: A Two-Year Case Study (Poster 24). *Peng He, Washington State University; Yu Xue, Washington State University; Namsoo Shin, Michigan State University; Shenghai Dai, Washington State University; Joseph S. Krajcik, Michigan State University*
25. Mapping out Collective Pedagogical Content Knowledge of Teaching with Living Organisms in Biology Classes (Poster 25). *Leroy Großmann, Freie Universität Berlin; Maren Koberstein-Schwarz, IPN*
26. Modeling the Process of Generating Scientific Observations for Sensemaking in the Field (Poster 26). *Lauren Barth-Cohen, University of Utah; Adrian L. Adams, University of Utah; Sarah Braden, Utah State University; Lynne Zummo, University of Utah; Holly Godsey, University of Utah; Kaitlyn Kinshella, University of Utah*
27. Teaching What They Don't Know: Baseline Analysis of Elementary Preservice Teachers' Science Content and Pedagogical Knowledge (Poster 27). *Jingyun Wu, Indiana University; Gholamreza Shamsi Pour, Indiana University; Fidelis Onwunanyi, Indiana University; Adam V. Maltese, Indiana University*

77.074-4. Division G: Section 4-Policies, Matterring, and Praxis Poster Session. Division G - Social Context of Education; Poster Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall -

Exhibit Hall A; 1:45-3:15pm

Posters:

28. Mapping Viewpoint Diversity Discourse Around Higher Education: From Matters of Fact to Matters of Concern (Poster 28). *Milad Mohebbali, University of Nebraska - Lincoln*
29. Navigating anti-DEI legislation as diversity affairs professionals in academic medicine in the Midwest: A collaborative critical autoethnography (Poster 29). *Sacha Sharp, Indiana University; Tiffinie Snowden, NA; Niki Messmore, Indiana University - Indianapolis; Amy Ribera, Indiana University*
30. Reclaiming Canceled Futures: The Interpretive Value of STEM Education Grants in Defining Scientific Research (Poster 30). *Kristina Kramarczuk, University of Maryland; Danielle Gervais Sodani, American University*
31. Strategizing for Academic Survival: Academic-Oriented Doctoral Students' Practices in China's Evaluation System (Poster 31). *Xiran Xiong, East China Normal University*
32. Who Gives More Support? Curvilinear Patterns in Parental Involvement by Class (Poster 32). *Hyevin Shin, University of Florida*
33. Becoming a Listening School: A Grounded Theory of Student-Adult Collaboration (Poster 33). *Jennifer Sneddon Chace, University of Southern Maine*
34. "But it's still called the boys' field": Female teachers as extracurricular advisors in rural schools (Poster 34). *Holly Marcolina, SUNY Potsdam*
35. "Cosmopolitan Virtues" in Action: a Qualitative Study of Students' Experiences of Visits to International Organizations (Poster 35). *Yiwen Wang, East China Normal University; Chunhui Yan, East China Normal University*
36. Evolving Discourses on Cyberbullying Intervention: A Meta-analysis(2014-2024) (Poster 36). *Jung Won Hyun, Ewha Womans University; Anna Lee, Ewha Womans University*
37. "Is It Equitable?": Math Leveling & Whiteness As Property In A Diversifying District (Poster 37). *Briana Markoff, University of Maine at Farmington; Sheila Orr, University of Tennessee*
38. Responding After: Campus Racism, Student Activism, and Institutional "Legacy" (Poster 38). *Katherine S. Cho, Loyola University Chicago; Jiaming James Zhou, Loyola University Chicago*

77.074-5. Division J Section 6: Poster Session. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Poster Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 1:45-3:15pm

Posters:

39. Academic Rankings and Public Accountability in Higher Education: A Comparative Study of São Paulo and California (Poster 39). *André Felipe Dutra Martins Rocha Elias, University of São Paulo*

40. Advancing the Critical AI Literacy and Self-Efficacy among Higher Education & Student Affairs Professionals (Poster 40). *Virginia Byrne, Morgan State University; Reyniak Richards, Morgan State University*
41. Countering the Unforgettable History of Exclusion: Inclusive Postsecondary Education for Students with Intellectual Disability (Poster 41). *Tamara H. Shetron, Texas State University*
42. Power, Property, and the Campus Conquest: Historiographical Perspectives on Higher Education and Eminent Domain (Poster 42). *Jaden Alexandra Mikoulinskii, University of Georgia; Jordan Mackenzie Mitchell, University of Georgia*
43. Presence of Inclusive Statements on R1 Institutions of Higher Education's Websites (Poster 43). *YeVonne Allen, Truckee Meadows Community College; Lynda R. Wiest, University of Nevada - Reno*
44. Sustainable Development in Higher Education: The Connotation, Characteristics, and Construction Paths of Sustainability University (Poster 44). *YIJING LYU, Nanjing Normal University*
45. Unpacking Discursive and Affective Functions of Whiteness to Construct a New Vision for Education Research (Poster 45). *Royel M. Johnson, University of Southern California; Marcus Maximus Martin, University of Southern California; Mya Haynes, USC; Alexia Oduro, University of Southern California*

77.074-6. Generative AI in Teacher Education: Innovations in Preparation, Practice, and Pedagogy. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 1:45-3:15pm

Posters:

46. Bibliometric Analysis of Generative AI in Teacher Education: Publication Trends and Thematic Clusters (Poster 46). *Shuman Wang, Stanford University; Ari Jiayu An, Stanford University; ziyue wang, Stanford University*
47. Exploring Hong Kong kindergarten teachers' technology integration practices (AI) in the classroom to support the needs of L1 and L2 Chinese language learners (Poster 47). *Yanling Zhou, The Education University of Hong Kong; Michelle Neumann, Southern Cross University; Min Zhu, The Education University of Hong Kong*
48. Generative AI in Teacher Preparation: A Mixed-Methods Study of the Classroom Coach Simulation (Poster 48). *Priya Sharma, Pennsylvania State University; Jacob Holster, Pennsylvania State University; Aaron Knochel, Pennsylvania State University; Jose Sandoval-Llanos, Pennsylvania State University; Fouz Aljameel, Pennsylvania State University*
49. Generative AI's Impact on Pre-service Teachers' Instructional Design: A Human-Computer Interaction Empirical Study (Poster 49). *Xu Wang, East China Normal*

University; Yu Chen, East China Normal University; Xiaohua Yu

50. Investigating Pre-Service Educators' Metacognitive Engagement with A GenAI System for Individualized Education Programs (Poster 50). *Ling Zhang, University of Wyoming; Tiffany Hunt, University of Wyoming; Haidee A. Jackson, University of Texas - Permian Basin; Sohyun Yang, Fort Hays State University; Jennifer Krause, University of Wyoming*
51. Preservice Teachers' Pedagogical Agency in the Remixing of AI Generated Lesson Plans (Poster 51). *Ashlynn Kogut, Texas A&M University; Sharon D. Matthews, Texas A&M University*

77.074-7. Switching Into and Out of Special Education Teacher (SET) Positions: Evidence from Texas. Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 1:45-3:15pm

77.074-8. Literacy in Afghan Refugee Families. Division G - Social Context of Education; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 1:45-3:15pm

Poster:

52. Daughters as "guiding lights" of literacy in Afghan refugee families in Pakistan (Poster 52). *Assadullah Sadiq, California State University - Channel Islands*

77.074-9. Standardized Tests as Gatekeepers. Division G - Social Context of Education; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 1:45-3:15pm

Poster:

53. Standardized Tests as Gatekeepers: LTELs' Self-Positioning and Resistance (Poster 53). *Huseyin Uysal, The Education University of Hong Kong*

77.075. e-Lightning Ed-Talk Session 18 - Stage 1. AERA e-Lightning Ed-Talks; AERA Ed Talk
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Exhibit Hall A - Stage 1; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

What Affects How Pre-service and In-service Teachers Rate Elementary Students' Creativity?: Demographic and Psychological Interactions (Stage 1, 1:50 PM). *Softia Kagan, University of Georgia; Denis Dumas, University of Georgia*
Students, Colleagues, and Principals as Contexts Shaping Teacher Self-Efficacy, Instruction, and Job Satisfaction (Stage 1, 1:59 PM). *Jenny Chaehyun Park, Korea University - Brain and Motivation Research Institute; Suyeon Gen Kim, Korea University - Brain and Motivation Research Institute; Jiwon Kim, Korea University - Brain and*

Motivation Research Institute; Patricia A. Alexander, University of Maryland; Mimi Bong, Korea University

Promotion and Prevention Motivation as Predictors of Students' Study Strategies in Math and Social Science (Stage 1, 2:08 PM). *Vishal Easwar, Boston College; Cristina D. Zepeda, Vanderbilt University; Meghan Coughlan, Boston College; David B. Miele, Boston College*

Injecting utility value in a microbiology class for undergraduate nursing students (Stage 1, 2:17 PM). *Vanessa Zhang, The Ohio State University; Rylan Deer, The Ohio State University; Huy Nguyen, The Ohio State University; Shirley L. Yu, The Ohio State University; Andrew Holmes Perry, The Ohio State University; Wonjoon Cha, The Ohio State University; Arianna Henning, The Ohio State University; Kimiko Ching, The Ohio State University; Michelle R. Richard, The Ohio State University*

Eye Tracking and Stimulated Recall Evidence of Young Readers' Metacognitive Processes in Science Picture Book Reading (Stage 1, 2:26 PM). *Zhujun Jiang, Shanghai Jiao Tong University; Tairui Song, East China Normal University; JIAYAN TEY, Shanghai Jiao Tong University; Feng-Kuang Chiang, Shanghai Jiao Tong University*

A Video-Based Category System for Identifying Adaptive Teaching Interactions in Elementary Mathematics (Stage 1, 2:35 PM). *Anne-Kathrin Buttchereyt, Bergische University St Wuppertal; Claudia Kastens, University of Wuppertal*

Where the Rocks Grow: Using photovoice and nature journaling to investigate student experiences in study-abroad (Stage 1, 2:44 PM). *Kelly Feille, University of Oklahoma; Cian Brown, University of Oklahoma*

The Role of Executive Functions in Reading Development: A Longitudinal Multilevel Modeling Approach (Stage 1, 2:53 PM). *Jieun Park, Middle Tennessee State University; Amy Elleman, Middle Tennessee State University; Yucheng Cao, Middle Tennessee State University*

Navigating the International Baccalaureate Journey: Challenges and Opportunities Perceived by High School Students and Alumni (Stage 1, 3:02 PM). *Xiao-Yin Chen, University of Tennessee; Kai Zhuang Shum, University of Tennessee; Chloe Muller, University of Tennessee; Amber Rosamond, University of Tennessee; Sophie Kronenberger, University of Tennessee; Madina Kholnazarova, University of Tennessee*

Chair: *Danette Waller McKinley, Foundation for Advancement of International Medical Education and Research*

77.076. e-Lightning Ed-Talk Session 18 - Stage 2. AERA e-Lightning Ed-Talks; AERA Ed Talk
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Exhibit Hall A - Stage 2; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Teaching Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning to Non-Major Students at University: A Scoping Review (Stage 2, 1:50 PM). *Oguz Koklu, Bogazici University; Muhammet Şahal, Yildiz Technical University; Merve Dede, Istanbul*

Beykent University

Unpacking the Psychometric Properties of Computational Thinking Measure (Stage 2, 1:59 PM). *Shaf Ahmed, Utah State University; David F. Feldon, Utah State University*

Modeling Science and Shaping Attitudes: Physical Computational Model and Mentorship in STEM+C Learning (Stage 2, 2:08 PM). *Jiajia Du, Texas A&M University; Ting Liu, Texas A&M University; Tanush Yarram, Texas A&M University; Kirti Sagar Gadde, Texas A&M University; Rebecca Ward, Texas A&M University; Rebecca Jean Schlegel, Texas A&M University*

Cascading Peer Mentoring in High School, Middle School, and Elementary School Computer Science Classrooms (Stage 2, 2:17 PM). *Elena Novak, Kent State University; Jason D. Schenker, Kent State University; Gözde McLaughlin, Kent State University; Sima Ahmadi, Kent State University; Yibei Guo, Kent State University; Rui Liu, Kent State University; Lisa A. Borgerding, Kent State University*

Navigating anti-DEI legislation as diversity affairs professionals in academic medicine in the Midwest: A collaborative critical autoethnography (Stage 2, 2:26 PM). *Sacha Sharp, Indiana University; Tiffinie Snowden, NA; Niki Messmore, Indiana University - Indianapolis; Amy Ribera, Indiana University*

Who Gives More Support? Curvilinear Patterns in Parental Involvement by Class (Stage 2, 2:35 PM). *Hyevin Shin, University of Florida*

Becoming a Listening School: A Grounded Theory of Student-Adult Collaboration (Stage 2, 2:44 PM). *Jennifer Sneddon Chace, University of Southern Maine*

"But it's still called the boys' field": Female teachers as extracurricular advisors in rural schools (Stage 2, 2:53 PM). *Holly Marcolina, SUNY Potsdam*

Responding After: Campus Racism, Student Activism, and Institutional "Legacy" (Stage 2, 3:02 PM). *Katherine S. Cho, Loyola University Chicago; Jiaming James Zhou, Loyola University Chicago*

Chair: *Carla D. O'Connor, University of Michigan*

77.077. e-Lightning Ed-Talk Session 18 - Stage 3. AERA e-Lightning Ed-Talks; AERA Ed Talk
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Exhibit Hall A - Stage 3; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Characterizing In-the-moment Scaffolding in Supporting Students' Models Interlocking During Phenomenon-Driven Science Instruction (Stage 3, 1:50 PM). *Idris Solola, Utah State University; Mimi M. Recker, Utah State University; Quentin Bidy, University of Colorado - Boulder*

Countering the Unforgettable History of Exclusion: Inclusive Postsecondary Education for Students with Intellectual Disability (Stage 3, 2:08 PM). *Tamara H. Shetron, Texas State University*

Power, Property, and the Campus Conquest: Historiographical

Perspectives on Higher Education and Eminent Domain (Stage 3, 2:17 PM). *Jaden Alexandra Mikoulinskii, University of Georgia*

Presence of Inclusive Statements on R1 Institutions of Higher Education's Websites (Stage 3, 2:26 PM). *YeVonne Allen, Truckee Meadows Community College; Lynda R. Wiest, University of Nevada - Reno*

Sustainable Development in Higher Education: The Connotation, Characteristics, and Construction Paths of Sustainability University (Stage 3, 2:35 PM). *YIJING LYU, Nanjing Normal University*

Unpacking Discursive and Affective Functions of Whiteness to Construct a New Vision for Education Research (Stage 3, 2:44 PM). *Royel M. Johnson, University of Southern California; Marcus Maximus Martin, University of Southern California; Mya Haynes, USC; Alexia Oduro, University of Southern California*

Bibliometric Analysis of Generative AI in Teacher Education: Publication Trends and Thematic Clusters (Stage 3, 2:53 PM). *Shuman Wang, Stanford University; Ari Jiayu An, Stanford University; ziyue wang, Stanford University*

Preservice Teachers' Pedagogical Agency in the Remixing of AI Generated Lesson Plans (Stage 3, 3:02 PM). *Ashlynn Kogut, Texas A&M University; Sharon D. Matthews, Texas A&M University*

Chair: *Uma Mazyck Jayakumar, University of California - Riverside*

Uncategorized Sessions

77.078. AERA Research in Progress Roundtable Session Four. AERA Sessions; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
1:45-3:15pm

77.078. Research-in-Progress RT004 (Saturday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Building Foundational Literacy Skills in Project-Based Learning Classes. *Marco Chacon, University of California - San Diego*

Humanizing Science: An Empathetic Approach to Sustaining Inquiry Cycles. *Marwa Crisp, Cobb County School District*
Integrating Practical Units into Instruction: Project-Based Learning in the Late 19th and Early 20th Centuries. *Cassie Ji, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

The Art of Guiding Learning: PBL, PJBL, and Assessment. *Portia Amoah-Danquah, Washington State University*

Chair: *Nadia Behizadeh, Georgia State University*

77.078. Research-in-Progress RT006 (Saturday). Research in

Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

A door to the future: A Case Study in Exploratory and Culturally Sustaining Theater Curriculum. *Verónica Meza, San Jose State University*

AI Education through Somatic Curriculum, Affective Pedagogy, and Speculative Design. *Mackayla Kelsey*

Intertwining Music, Nature, and Culture: Hua'er and Music Education in Forest Schools. *Zixuan Yang, University of Oxford*

Listening to Artists: MMR Study of Material Responsiveness as a Compound Pathway to Creative Thinking. *Jennifer Ruth Hoyden, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Chair: *Laurence Parker, University of Utah*

77.078. Research-in-Progress RT016 (Saturday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Encouraging Children's Curiosity and Learning Through AI-generated Media: The Influence of Character Similarity and Culture. *Hyunyoung Cho, Boston College; Elida V. Laski, Boston College; Marina Vasilyeva, Boston College*

Exploring Young Children's Problem-Solving Processes with Educational Robots: A Multi-Case Study. *Cong Liu, Binghamton University - SUNY*

Co-Designing Interdependence: Participation Pathways in Mixed-Ability Playground Activity. *Isabella Teresa Seccia, University of California - Irvine; Jessica Blake-West, Boston College; Kelsyann Cervera, University of California - Irvine; Kat Allen, Tufts University; Andres Sebastian Bustamante, University of California - Irvine; June Ahn, University of California - Irvine*

The Impact of Guided Play on Executive Function in Early Childhood: A Pilot Study. *Seoyeon Sohn, University of Delaware; Roberta Michnick Golinkoff, University of Delaware*

The Development of 21st Century Skills in Kindergarten Students During Constructive Play. *Jennifer O'Dougherty, Long Island University - C.W. Post Campus*

Chair: *Barbara Rogoff, University of California - Santa Cruz*

77.078. Research-in-Progress RT017 (Saturday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

A Case Study on Kindergartener's Achievement Emotions during Mathematical Learning. *Julia Paige Pfeiffer, University of Virginia; Laura Kohler, University of Virginia; Traci Shizu Kutaka, University of Virginia*

Assessing the Quality of Preschool Writing Instruction: Development and Preliminary Findings from the tWRITE Measure. *Müge Ongur, Georgia State University; Gary E. Bingham, Georgia State University*

Early Executive Function as a Predictor of Later Academic Achievement. *Chase Haney, California State University - Fullerton; Sue Sy, California State University - Fullerton*

Exploring Bedtime Reading as a Mediator Between Maternal Depression and Preschoolers' Receptive Vocabulary. *Nicole Kingdon, Boston University*

Rethinking Family Empowerment Across Early Childhood Education, Intervention, and Special Education. *jiajia liu, Virginia Commonwealth University; Yaoying Xu, Virginia Commonwealth University*

Chair: *Theresa A. Thorkildsen, University of Illinois at Chicago*

77.078. Research-in-Progress RT026 (Saturday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Mimicking Gestures or Drawing: Which Better Supports Learning Statistics from Video? *Luke Rabelhofer, University of California - Riverside; Felipe Cruz, University of California - Riverside*

Multisensory Game-Based Learning for Mathematical Enrichment. *Sejin Pak, Korea University; HAE LI LEE, Korea University; Seoyeon Choi, Korea University; Yeongje Kim, Korea University; Insook Han, Korea University*

Teachers Developing Strategies for AI Integration in Mathematics Education within the I-TPACK Framework. *Merve KOCYIGIT GURBUZ, Southern Methodist University*

The Interplay of Self-Efficacy and Performance: Behavioral Insights from Digital Mathematics Learning. *Sarah Shaw, Vanderbilt University*

Using Random Forest and Multilevel Modeling to Uncover ICT Predictors of Mathematics in PISA 2022. *Linlin Li, McGill University; Yun Ma, Qingdao University; Zhengyu Yang, University of Hong Kong; Yiwen Yan, McGill University; Yimei Zhang, McGill University; Yajie Song, McGill University; Maria Cutumisu, McGill University*

Chair: *Gregory J. Kelly, University of Massachusetts - Amherst*

77.078. Research-in-Progress RT031 (Saturday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Beyond Belonging: A Mixed Methods Interrogation of Belonging and Latina Futures in STEM. *Stephanie E. Hertel, University of California - Santa Cruz*

Informal, Student-Led Sustainability Initiatives as Learning Spaces for Science and Engineering Students. *Midhat Noor Kiyani, McGill University; Limin Jao, McGill University*

The Enactment of Improvement Science in Higher Education. *Elizabeth Jones, University of Michigan*

Understanding Academic Advising and Its Impact on Black Women in STEM: A Sequential Mixed Methods Study. *Cheyenne Smith, Indiana University*

Voices of the Unheard - Women Of Color Undergraduates Majoring In STEM. *Robin Glassberg, New York University*

Chair: *Ebony O. McGee, Johns Hopkins University*

77.078. Research-in-Progress RT035 (Saturday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

A Raciolinguistic Analysis of the Linguaging Experiences of Racialized Bilinguals as They Transition to College. *Alexandra Federico McGrath, University of Colorado - Boulder*

Critical Allyship of Undergraduate White Men. *Grant D Batchelder, University of Arizona*

Leaving or Liberation: Exploring the Experiences of Black Student Affairs Professionals. *Terri Armstrong, California State University - Long Beach*

Unveiling and Moving Beyond the Margins: Exploring Black Women Preservice Teachers' Experiences at PWIs. *Kristina Jones, Pennsylvania State University*

Chair: *Yolanda Sealey-Ruiz, Teachers College, Columbia University*

77.078. Research-in-Progress RT046 (Saturday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Aquatic Safety Education for Elementary Students: A Systematic Review to Inform the Palekana Aquatics Academy. *Karl-Richard Hennebach, University of Hawai'i at Manoa*

Enhancing Learning Through Developing Transferrable Skills in General Psychology Courses. *Donna Arteaga Alvarez, University of California - Riverside; Hayden Schill Hendley, University of California - Riverside*

Teaching Between the Lines: How 3rd-5th Grade Teachers of Diverse Readers Navigate High-Quality Instructional Materials. *Marcie Jones, Claremont Graduate University*

Re-mediating Relations Through Co-design: Redistributing Researcher, Teacher, and Learner Expertise. *Molly C. Marek, University of Texas at Austin*

Chair: *Christine E. Sleeter, California State University - Monterey Bay*

77.078. Research-in-Progress RT050 (Saturday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;

1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

- Black Women of the South Carolina Sea Islands and the (Re)Construction of Black Education. *Amber Chevaughn Johnson, University of Maryland*
- Bridging Worlds: The Knowledge Pathways of Black American Women Teaching English as a Medium of Instruction in the UAE's Emirati-serving PreK-5 Context. *Andwatta Barnes, University of Michigan*
- Mentorship and Development of Black Women Teachers: Preliminary Findings from Studies in Progress. *Janelle Blackstone, American University; Dylan Ravdin, American University and Bronx Charter School for the Arts*

Chair: *Maisie L. Gholson, University of Michigan*

77.078. Research-in-Progress RT055 (Saturday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

- The Value of Musical Education: Perspectives from Students and Policy from Institutions. *Sophie Ailsa Lewis, Boston University*
- Translating the PhD: The Cultural Strengths Behind Latina PhD Students' Communication Approaches. *Brenda Rincon, University of California - Riverside; Jennifer Amador, University of California - Riverside; Elizabeth Serna, University of California - Riverside; Diamond Bravo, University of California - Riverside*
- The Rise of Higher Education Influencers: Digital Discourses on Contemporary College Life. *Olugbenga Joseph, Northwestern University*
- Academic Advising Experiences of Division I Black/African American Student-Athletes at Minority Serving Institutions (MSIs). *Jada Crocker, George Mason University; Ellen Drogin Rodgers, George Mason University*

Chair: *Omi Salas-SantaCruz, University of Utah*

77.078. Research-in-Progress RT058 (Saturday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

- Black Male Youths: Joy, Achievement, and Academic Success in the Face of Being Underestimated. *Thomas Flagg, Texas Christian University*
- Black Youth Resisting Carceral Schooling: Critical Hope, Radical Imagination, and Sociopolitical Development in Youth Organizing. *Shantell P. Missouri, UCLA*
- Perceived Linguistic Discrimination, Standard English Ideologies, and Academic Self-Efficacy among Black Native and Non-Native College Students. *Scheleck Rebecca Laraque, Howard University*

"They Don't Want to See Us Thrive": Counter-Narratives of

Black Boys' Educational Experiences Across 6th-12th Grade Schooling. *Vaughn I. Parham, University of Maryland*

Chair: *Felice J. Levine, AERA Emerita*

77.078. Research-in-Progress RT061 (Saturday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

- College and Career Readiness in Practice: An Ethnographic Study of College and Career Readiness Experiences and the Role of Support Systems in Promoting Success at a Lower-Income High School. *Jesica Lovelace, University of Central Florida*
- Empowering Future Educators: Praxeological Learning and High School Tutors' Attitudes Toward Teaching Careers. *Xavier L. Rozas, University of North Florida*
- "Seeing a Way Out": Studying Middle School Athletes' Interest and Mentorship Toward STEM Careers. *Arneshia LaShelle Bryant-Horn, University of California - Riverside*
- VR as a Digital Pathway: Empowering Brazilian Mothers through English Language Learning and Career Preparation. *Adriana S. Vianna, University of South Florida*

Chair: *Mark Warschauer, University of California - Irvine*

77.078. Research-in-Progress RT065 (Saturday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

- Exploring The Parental Attitude And Behavior On Using Smart Applications For Students With Learning Difficulties In Saudi Arabia. *Norah H. Alharbi, Indiana University*
- Parenting Styles, Parent-Child Communication, and Loneliness Among Chinese International Students: A Mixed-Methods Study. *Xiang Li, University of Pennsylvania*
- Developing Academic Skills with Technology. *Gloria James-Avalos, Ysleta Independent School District*

Chair: *Christian J. Faltis, Texas A&M International University*

77.078. Research-in-Progress RT071 (Saturday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

- Examining How Cross-State "Grow Your Own" Initiatives Bolster Multilingual Learner Teacher Pipelines. *Katherine M Shanahan, University of Pittsburgh*
- From Policy to Practice : Analyzing Ideology in Arizona's Language Policy. *Katie R. Clones, Arizona State University*
- Practiced Language Policy in a United States Secondary Spanish for Heritage Speakers Course. *Kara Marie Rash, University of Iowa*

Chair: *Judith L. Green, University of California - Santa Barbara*

77.078. Research-in-Progress RT073 (Saturday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Punish, Prohibit, or Protect? Exploring Relationships Between School Division Policies and Anti-Racist Practice. *Chelsea Davis, University of Saskatchewan*

Working towards equity: The lived experiences of equity directors of color in predominantly and historically white suburban K-12 school districts. *Jamie A Holifield, University of Wisconsin - Milwaukee*

Chair: *Carol Camp Yeakey, Washington University in St. Louis*

Saturday, April 11th, 2:00 pm

SIG Sessions

78.010. It Is Our Duty to Win: Youth Organizing and the Struggle for Police-Free, Life-Affirming Schools in LA. SIG-Grassroots Community and Youth Organizing for Educational Justice; Off-Site Visit
Chuco's Justice Center, 7625 S. Central Ave, Los Angeles, CA 90001, Lobby; 2:00-5:00pm

Visit Leader: *David C. Turner III, University of California, Los Angeles*

Chair: *Uriel Serrano, University of Southern California*

Discussant: *Anibal Serrano, University of California - Irvine*

Saturday, April 11th, 3:45 pm

Governance Meetings and Events

79.001. AERA Research Advisory Committee: Closed Meeting. AERA Governance; Governance Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 513;
3:45-5:15pm

Chair: *Dorothy L. Espelage, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*

AERA Related Activities

79.010. 2026 AERA-Fellowship Program on the Study of Deeper Learning Meeting. AERA Related Activities; Board Meeting
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 514;

3:45-5:15pm

Chair: *George L. Wimberly, American Educational Research Association*

Presidential Sessions

79.011. Archiving Art as a Legacy to Preserve Pasts/Futures. AERA Presidential Session; Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 406AB;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Holding Space, Making Sound: Sanctuary, Memory, and the Pedagogy of Care. *Stevie D. Johnson, The Ohio State University*

Movement as a Site of Knowing Futurity. *Cierra Kaler-Jones, Rethinking Schools*

“Witness”: Coalitionally Bearing Witness to Envision Educational Futurities. *Ankhi Guha Thakurta, Boston College*

Growing Up Bronx. *Yolanda Sealey-Ruiz, Teachers College, Columbia University*

The Mighty Struggle: A Town Called Miracle. *John Jennings, University of California - Riverside*

Chairs: *Justin A. Coles, University of Massachusetts - Amherst; Darnel Degand, University of California - Davis; Grace D. Player, University of Connecticut*

Discussant: *James Haywood Rolling, Syracuse University*

79.012. Navigating Children's and Young Adult Literature in an Era of Contested Literacies: Possibilities for Education Research and Teaching. AERA Presidential Session; Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 408B;
3:45-5:15pm

Chair: *E. Sybil Durand, Arizona State University*

Participants: *James Joshua Coleman, Arizona State University; Angel Daniel Matos, Bowdoin College; Fabienne Doucet, New York University; Rafael Rogers, Clark University; Jung E. Kim, Lewis University; Autumn A. Griffin, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; shea wesley martin, The Ohio State University; Patricia Enciso, The Ohio State University; Ebony Elizabeth Thomas, University of Michigan; Jon M. Wargo, University of Michigan*

79.013. The 29th Conversations With Senior Scholars on Advancing Research and Professional Development Related to Black Education. AERA Presidential Session; Invited Roundtable

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;

3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

1. Means for Achieving and Thriving in Your Doctoral Program to Graduation (Table 1). *Kimberley Edelin Freeman, Howard University; Nicole Patton-Terry, Florida State University; Adrienne D. Dixson, Pennsylvania State University*
 2. Women of Color in Academe: The Difference Makers (Table 2). *Stephanie J. Rowley, University of Virginia; Saundra M Tomlinson-Clarke, Rutgers University; Olga M. Welch, Duquesne University*
 3. Men of Color in Academe: Roles that Must be Undertaken and Sustained (Table 3). *James D. Anderson, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Kofi Lomotey, Western Carolina University*
 4. Quantitative Research Shapes Educational Policy and Practice: Are You In?—Sylvia Johnson Table (Table 4). *Donald Easton-Brooks, University of Nevada - Reno; Toks S. Fashola, American University; Will J. Jordan, The Wallace Foundation*
 5. Addressing and Advancing the Role of Culture in Educational Research (Table 5). *Valerie Kinloch, Johnson C. Smith University; Carol D. Lee, Northwestern University*
 6. Expanding Progress, Advancement, Education and Research at our HBCUs (Table 6). *Fred A. Bonner, Prairie View A&M University; Lillian B. Poats, Texas Southern University; Paula Groves Price, North Carolina A&T State University*
 7. Advancing Equity Through Academic Leadership While Addressing Politics and New Culture Wars: Personal and Professional Challenges (Table 7). *Sonya Douglass, Teachers College, Columbia University; Carl A. Grant, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Howard C. Johnson, Syracuse University; Monika Williams Shealey, Temple University*
 8. Rich Career Opportunities in Non-Academic Jobs Off Campus and On-- Ronald D. Henderson Table (Table 8). *Mary E. Dilworth, Independent Researcher; Monica B. Mitchell, MERAssociates; Adriane E. L. Dorrington, National Education Association*
 9. Advancing as Graduate Students or Postdoctoral Fellows to Establish Productive Professional Careers-- Edgar G. Epps Table (Table 9). *James Earl Davis, Temple University; Carol Camp Yeakey, Washington University in St. Louis*
 10. Effective and Efficient Methods for Publishing (Table 10). *Gloria J. Ladson-Billings, University of Wisconsin - Madison; John B. Diamond, Brown University; Margaret Beale Spencer, University of Chicago*
 11. Developing Meaningful University-Public School Partnerships Coupled with Community-Based Research (Table 11). *Jerome E. Morris, University of Missouri - St. Louis; Bernard Oliver, Georgia Gwinnett College*
 12. Calling on Culturally Responsive Evaluators to Advance Equity and Social Betterment—Stafford L. Hood Table (Table 12). *Tamara Bertrand Jones, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Kevin E. Favor, Lincoln University; Jori N. Hall, University of Illinois at Chicago*
 13. The Politics of Knowledge and Educational Research—The Consequences of Reality (Table 13). *Linda Darling-Hammond, Learning Policy Institute; William F. Tate, Rutgers University*
 14. The Importance of and Approaches to Conducting Community-Based Research (Table 14). *Rich Milner, Vanderbilt University; Maisha T. Winn, Stanford University; Muhammad Khalifa, The Ohio State University*
 15. Targeting Areas of Educational Needs and Developing Effective Programs to Address Them (Table 15). *Tyrone C. Howard, University of California - Los Angeles; Darris Roshawn Means, Clemson University; Eboni M. Zamani-Gallaher, University of Pittsburgh*
 16. Centers, Institutes, and Laboratories: Strategies for Generating, Funding, and Managing Research and Develop Programs, Including Student-Based Programs (Table 16). *Caesar R Jackson, North Carolina Central University; Chance W. Lewis, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; James Moore, National Science Foundation; Jerlando F.L. Jackson, Michigan State University*
 17. Opportunities in International Educational Research, Program Development, and Collaborations (Table 17). *Joyce E. King, Georgia State University; Gaëtane Jean-Marie, Rowan University; Stephen D. Hancock, North Carolina A&T State University; Victoria Showunmi, University College London - IOE*
 18. Advancing Student Academic Success through Research and Program Development (Table 18). *Timothy K. Eatman, Rutgers University - Newark; Shaun R. Harper, University of Southern California; Ivory A. Toldson, Howard University*
 19. Examining Pathway to a College of Education Deanship: Expectations, Challenges, and Rewards (Table 19). *Robert Q. Berry, Indiana University; Marvin Lynn, University of Colorado - Denver; Kimberly A. White-Smith, University of San Diego; Laura P. Kohn-Wood, University of Miami*
 20. The Needed Attention for the Burgeoning AI Impact on Education and Education Research (Table 20). *Kenneth Alonzo Anderson, Howard University; Keena N. Arbuthnot, Rutgers University; Talitha M. Washington, Howard University*
 21. Surviving, Achieving, and Thriving in Academe (Table 21). *Walter R. Allen, University of California - Los Angeles; Wanda J. Blanchett, Rutgers University*
- Chairs: *Henry T. Frierson, University of Florida; Rodney K. Hopson, American University*

Honorary President Edmund W. Gordon Series

- 79.014. Finding the Future of Assessment in the Service of Learning.** AERA Honorary President Edmund W. Gordon Series; Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 403B;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants: *Eva L. Baker, University of California - Los Angeles; Howard T. Everson, City University of New York; Andrew Ho, Harvard University; Jennifer Randall, University of Michigan*

Moderator: *Stephen G. Sireci, University of Massachusetts - Amherst*

AERA Sessions

79.015. Reclaiming Our Regional History: An Intergenerational Plática with Student, Parent, and Teacher Activist in Williams v. California. Spotlight on Los Angeles and the Region; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 404AB;
3:45-5:15pm

Chair: *Anna M. Ortiz, California State University - Long Beach*

Participant: *Lluliana Alonso, California State University - Long Beach*

Discussant: *Daniel Gilbert Solorzano, University of California - Los Angeles*

Committee Sessions

79.016. A Tribe Called “Quest”. Remembering Histories and Shaping Futures in Experiential and Global Learning. Graduate Student Council; Invited Speaker Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 402A;
3:45-5:15pm

Chair: *Darren Clarke, Rutgers University*

Panelists: *Ajua Kouadio, Rutgers University; Mahadi Walrond, Rutgers University; Ashley Lipscomb, Rutgers University; Shari Cunningham, West Chester University of Pennsylvania*

Division Sessions

79.017. Building Capacity and Coherence for Instructional Improvement and Systemwide Reform. Division A - Administration; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, La Brea; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Aligning an Approach to Principal Efficacy with School Improvement Urgency: A Design-Based Implementation Research Study. *Paula Tharp, Mississippi State University; Michelle Forman, SERP Institute*

Consulting without Consequences: The Absence of Accountability in Educational Consulting. *Matthew S. McCluskey, University of Vermont; Elizabeth J. Adams, University of Vermont; Lindsey A. Cox, University of Vermont*

Principal Mediation of Pre-K to 3 Coherence: Cross-Case Insights from Two Districts. *Melanie Muskin, Northwestern University; Cynthia E. Coburn, Northwestern University; Laila Barcenas, Northwestern University; Nalini Khurana, Northwestern University; Angel Xiao Bohannon, NORC at the University of Chicago; Abigail Stein, Carnegie Mellon University; Emma Rose Relyea, Northwestern University*
Unpacking System-Level Conditions for Sustained Reform in Catholic Schools. *Aashna Khurana, Boston College*

Chair: *Xiu Cravens, Vanderbilt University*

Discussant: *Candice Bocala, Harvard University*

79.018. Disruptive Historicizing and Futurity in Curriculum Theorizing. Division B - Curriculum Studies; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304A;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Apocalypse Pedagogies: Teaching (in) the Eclipse of Meaning. *Ralph J. McCoy, Purdue University; Jake Burdick, Purdue University*

Between Empire and Screens: Coloniality and ‘Unpublic’ Pedagogy in Chinese Lesbianism. *Xun Ril Li, University of Toronto - OISE*

The Pernicious Whiteness of Coloniality: Genealogizing to Locate the “Nowhere” of Global Curricula. *James C. Jupp, University of Texas - Rio Grande Valley; Todd Alan Price, National Louis University*

Toward Historicized Grammars of Educational Accountability: Reckoning with Historical Trauma, Memory, Debt and the Reparative. *Grace A. Livingston, University of Puget Sound*

Chair: *Brandon L. Fox, University of Wisconsin Stevens Point*

Discussant: *Kevin D. Lam, Drake University*

79.019. AI and Youth Learning Across the Globe: Insights from Four Large-Scale Surveys. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Symposium
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Beaudry A; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Does Access to Generative AI for Learning Change High School Students’ Academic Self-Concept? *Echo Zexuan Pan, Harvard University; Trisha Thomas, Harvard University; Danny Glick, Oranim College of Education; Ying Xu, Harvard University*

Understanding Who Uses AI Tutoring: A Nationally Benchmarked Study of Answer.AI Users. *Max Lu, Harvard University; Ying Xu, Harvard University*

Adolescent AI Use and Developmental Needs: A Self-Determination Theory Perspective. *Zhiying Yue, Harvard University; Hannah Chidekel, Harvard University; Michael Rich, Harvard University; David S Bickham, Boston Children’s Hospital*

Chinese and American Children’s Internet Attitudes: A Multi-group Confirmatory Factor Analysis. *Lauren Girouard-Hallam, University of Michigan; Yu Tong, Jiangnan*

University; Fuxing Wang, Central China Normal University; Judith H Danoviich, University of Louisville

Chair: *Ying Xu, Harvard University*

Discussant: *Ying Xu, Harvard University*

79.020. Examining Mathematics Teaching Practices. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Beaudry B; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Exploring Teacher Verbal Feedback in Chinese Primary Mathematics Classrooms: A Video-Based Study. *Jingwen Wang, Institute of Curriculum and Instruction East China Normal University; Hao Xie, Institute of Curriculum and Instruction East China Normal University; Wenye Zhou, Institute of Curriculum and Instruction East China Normal University*

How Teaching Practices Relate to Early Mathematics Competencies: A Non-linear Modeling Perspective. *Christina D. Mulcahy, University of Denver; Yixiao Dong, University of California - Santa Barbara; Douglas H. Clements, University of Denver; Julie Sarama, University of Denver*

Instructional Adaptations of Evidence-Based Mathematics Intervention for Tier 3: A Qualitative Study of Teacher Practices. *Charissa Richards, University of Missouri; Syeda Sharjina Akther, University of Texas at Austin; Megyn Elizabeth Martin, University of Missouri; Emily A. Short, Southern Methodist University; Leanne R. Ketterlin-Geller, Southern Methodist University; Sarah R. Powell, University of Texas at Austin; Erica S. Lembke, University of Missouri*

Scaling cognitive principles to large-scale educational contexts: Feasibility and Lessons Learned. *Drew Barrett, WestEd; Bryan Matlen, WestEd*

Chair: *Jui-Teng Li, Appalachian State University*

Discussant: *Walter M. Stroup, University of Massachusetts - Dartmouth*

79.021. Reimagining Researcher-Participant Relations in Engineering and Computing Education. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Structured Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 515A; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

1. Paper 1: Elevating Students as Equal Partners in Research and Dissemination Through Storytelling Workshops (Poster 1). *Monica Elaine Cardella, Florida International University; Dorothy Decontee Gocol, Florida International University*
2. Paper 2: Pláticas as Pedagogies of Resistance: Cultivating Critical Consciousness in Engineering Students at a Hispanic Serving Institution (Poster 2). *Joel Alejandro Mejia, University of Cincinnati*
3. Paper 3: Making Space for Identity Work in Engineering through Design Research (Poster 3). *Yume Menghe Xu, Tufts*

University; Brian E. Gravel, Tufts University

4. Paper 4: Climate Tech Journalism: Engineering Climate Futures through the Voices of Multilingual and Multidialectal Youth (Poster 4). *L. Clara Mabour, Tufts University; Greses Perez, Tufts University; Kristen Wendell, Tufts University; Fatima Rahman, Tufts University; Chelsea Andrews, Tufts University*
 5. Paper 5: Using Art to Reflect and Reimagine Undergraduate Engineering Education (Poster 5). *Stephen D. Secules, University of New Mexico; Nivedita Kumar, Florida International University*
 6. Paper 6: What does it mean to design for people and communities, rather than disciplines? (Poster 6). *Brian E. Gravel, Tufts University; Dionne N. Champion, University of Florida; Eli Tucker-Raymond, Boston University; Amon D. Millner, Franklin W. Olin College of Engineering; Christopher G. Wright, Drexel University; Ayana Allen-Handy, Hofstra University; L. Clara Mabour, Tufts University*
 7. Paper 7: Maintaining or Dismantling Borders in Community-Based Projects: Reflections from a Study Abroad Program in Colombia (Poster 7). *Trevion S. Henderson, Tufts University; Collette P Higgins, Tufts University*
 8. Paper 8: Learning from Multilingual and Multidialectal Communities: The Everyday Origins of Engineering Practices (Poster 8). *Greses Perez, Tufts University; Philippa Eshun, Tufts University; G.R. Marvez, Tufts University; L. Clara Mabour, Tufts University; Pragye Shrestha, Tufts University; Taisha Pierre, Tufts University; Mia Jimenez, Tufts University; Luis F. Suarez, Tufts University*
- Chairs: *Brian E. Gravel, Tufts University; Monica Elaine Cardella, Florida International University; Greses Perez, Tufts University*

Discussant: *Ananda M. Marin, University of California - Los Angeles*

79.022. Transforming Early Science Teaching Through Professional Learning. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Level 3, Avalon; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

- Deconstructing Teacher Response for Equitable Instruction in Elementary Science. *Linda K. Preminger, California State University, East Bay; Kathryn N. Hayes, California State University - East Bay*
- Infant/Toddler-Second Grade Clinical Educators' Utilization of Traditional versus Reform-Oriented Science Teaching Practices. *Rosa Julia Mykyta-Chomsky, University of Delaware; Jennifer Gallo-Fox, University of Delaware*
- Inquiry-Based Science Instruction in Lower Primary Schools: Evaluating Teacher Practices under a Standards-Based Curriculum Framework. *Isaac Buabeng, University of Cape Coast; Bridget Amo-Darko, University of Education - Winneba*

Reimagining communities of practice in elementary science.
Sinead C. Brien, University of South Carolina - Upstate;
David Stroupe, University of Utah

Starting Points Matter: Unpacking Differences in Elementary
Science Teachers Change in Professional Development.
Singith Nuwanga Perera, Virginia Commonwealth
University; Christine Lee Bae, Virginia Commonwealth
University; Linda K. Preminger, California State University,
East Bay; Kathryn N. Hayes, California State University -
East Bay; Rachel Niemira, Virginia Commonwealth
University

Chair: *David Stroupe, University of Utah*

Discussant: *Dessy S. Stoycheva, University of Northern Iowa*

**79.023. Virtuous or Viceful? How K-12 and Undergraduate
Students Use and Perceive Generative AI.** Division C -
Learning and Instruction; Symposium
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, San Gabriel C; 3:45-
5:15pm

Participants:

Evidence of Students Resorting to GenAI in an Adaptive
Learning and Assessment System. *Hasan Uzun, McGraw-*
Hill; Jeffrey Matayoshi, McGraw-Hill; Eric Cosyn,
McGraw-Hill; Eyad Kurd-Misto, McGraw-Hill; Sina
Rismanchian, University of California - Irvine

Generative AI and Integrity: A Mixed Methods Examination of
Student Perceptions and Experience. *Annie Camey Kuo,*
Stanford University; Ruishi Chen, Stanford University;
Maria Romero, Stanford University; Victor R. Lee, Stanford
University; Denise C. Pope, Stanford University; Sarah
Miles, Challenge Success

From Brainstorming to Editing: Student Perspectives on the
Ethics of Generative AI Assistance in the Writing Process.
Vanessa Dennen, Florida State University; Zhongyu Wang,
Florida State University

Measuring Students' Use of AI in Short Answer Questions in a
Course on Intellectual Virtues. *Peter Liu, University of*
California - Irvine; Sina Rismanchian, University of
California - Irvine; Gabe Avakian Orona, Boston College;
Shayan Doroudi, University of California - Irvine

Extended Cognition and the AI Challenge to Higher Education.
Duncan Pritchard, University of California, Irvine

Chairs: *Shayan Doroudi, University of California - Irvine; Denise*
C. Pope, Stanford University

Discussant: *Samaa Haniya, Pepperdine University*

79.024. Advising Around Postsecondary Pathways. Division E -
Counseling and Human Development; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 301A;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Dual Enrollment Advising. *Nina Arshavsky, University of North*
Carolina - Greensboro

Expanding Career-Focused Advising: Findings from Two

Qualitative Studies. *Bryan C. Hutchins, University of North*
Carolina - Greensboro; Julie A. Edmunds, University of
North Carolina - Greensboro

Impacts of Career-Focused Advising. *Christine Mulhern,*
RAND; Brian M. Phillips, RAND Corporation

High School Advising: Exploring Students' Perceptions of
School-Based Support for College and Career Transitions.
John Sludden, New York University; James J. Kemple, New
York University

Chair: *Nina Arshavsky, University of North Carolina - Greensboro*

Discussant: *Marissa R. Moreno, Lee College*

**79.025. Early Learning and Development: Tools, Contexts, and
Outcomes.** Division E - Counseling and Human
Development; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 303B;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

The Causal Effects of the Denver Preschool Program's Tuition
Credit on Children's Kindergarten Readiness. *Vi-Nhuan Le,*
NORC at the University of Chicago; Diana Schaack,
University of Colorado - Denver; Cristal Cisneros, Denver
Preschool Program; Jolene Castillo Gregory, Denver Public
Schools

Development and Psychometric Testing of a Video-gamified
Assessment of Prosocial Behavior: vSchool. *Joy Roos,*
University of Missouri; Christi Crosby Bergin, University of
Missouri; Wes Bonifay, University of Missouri; Nathanael
Light, University of Missouri; Afiah Fozi, University of
Missouri; JG Griffin, University of Missouri

Capturing Mattering in the Elementary School Classroom: A
Rasch Modeling Study of the Mattering to Teachers Scale.
Camila Polanco, University of Delaware; Roderick L.
Carey, University of Delaware; Tracy Waasdorp, Children's
Hospital of Philadelphia; Nicholas S. Bell, University of
Connecticut; Valerie Earnshaw, University of Delaware; Tia
Navelene Barnes, University of Delaware

Evaluating Early Childhood Personal-Social Development: A
Bioecological Analysis of Proposition 10 Funding Impact.
Jianjun Wang, California State University - Bakersfield

Investigating Time Invariance of the HOME Inventory in
Disadvantaged Families. *Zhenqiao Yang, Southeast Missouri*
State University; Amelia Miramonti, University of Nebraska
- Lincoln; Dan Wang, University of Oklahoma; Qingyu
Jiang, University of Nebraska - Lincoln

Chair: *Anupama Joshi, California State University - Dominguez*
Hills

**79.026. If Black Women Were Free: The Politics and Pedagogy
of Black Power from the U.S. to the U.K.** Division F -
Historical Inquiry in Education; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 306A;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

“You Gotta Keep On, Keeping On”: Harlem’s Fight for Black Minds. *Terri N. Watson, City College of New York - CUNY*

Toni Cade Bambara: Tools of Resistance from an Activist-Pedagogue. *Makeba Lavan, Grinnell College*

Black Feminist Praxis and Pedagogy Under Fire. *Lucien Baskin, Graduate Center - CUNY*

We Anchor Ourselves in History’: Counter-Schooling, Resistance, and Revolt in the Metropole. *Shreya Sunderram, Graduate Center - CUNY*

Pedagogy & The Politics of Self-Esteem in British Black Supplementary Schools. *Rosa-Johan Uddoh, Royal College of Art, London*

Chair: *Robert P. Robinson, CUNY - John Jay College of Criminal Justice*

Discussant: *Maithreyi Rajeshkumar, The Graduate Center, CUNY*

79.027. Abolitionist Experiments in Research: Enacting an Abolitionist Praxis in a National Study in Youth Prisons.

Division G - Social Context of Education; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 309;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Shaking Abolitionist Foundations: Building a Study in Prisons Against Prisons. *Subini Ancy Annamma, Stanford University; Greg Prieto, University of San Diego*

Collective Embodied Abolitionist Disposition, Reflection, and Data Collection in Youth Carceral Facilities. *Brianna Marche' Harvey, California State University - Fullerton; Brian Cabral, University of Texas at Austin; Michael O'Key, Stanford University*

Abolishing Carceral Geographies: Reclaiming Third Spaces in the Educational Lives of Incarcerated Young People. *Kaleb Germinaro, University of Illinois at Chicago; Veronica Velez, Western Washington University; Sophie D'Souza, Stanford University*

Resisting Positivist Framing of Incarcerated Youth: Making Sense of QuantCrit and Abolition. *Candice Jeehae Kim, Stanford University*

Chair: *David O. Stovall, University of Illinois at Chicago*

Discussant: *David O. Stovall, University of Illinois at Chicago*

79.028. Unforgetting Newcomer Experiences, Knowledges, and Identities: Humanizing and Future-making Pedagogies across Canada and the U.S.

Division G - Social Context of Education; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 301B;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Immigrant-background Children Composing Multilingual Multimodal Identity Texts as a Culturally Sustaining Humanizing Practice in Canada. *Harini Rajagopal, University of British Columbia; Xiaoxiao Du, University of Manitoba*

School and Home Literacy Practices of a Refugee-background

Seventh Grader in the U.S. *Aijuan Cun, University of New Mexico*

Digital Storytelling with Teachers of Youth from Refugee Backgrounds: Honoring Assets, Life Journeys, and Relationships. *Amir Michalovich, University of Manitoba; Shawn Porteous, River East Transcona School Division*
Canadian Schools Benefiting from the Refugee-background Teachers’ Curricula and Pedagogies. *Sofia Noori, University of British Columbia*

Futuring Teacher Education: Community Partnerships with Refugee Families for Critical, Caring, and Joyful Learning. *Nermin Vehabovic, Elon University*

Chair: *Xiaoxiao Du, University of Manitoba*

Discussant: *Amir Michalovich, University of Manitoba*

79.029. Division H VP Session: From Policy to Practice: A Multi-Sector Approach to Responsible AI Integration in Education.

Division H - Research, Evaluation and Assessment in Schools; Paper Session
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor,
Wilshire Grand Ballroom II; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Navigating AI Implementation in Public Agencies: Regulatory Compliance, Readiness Assessment, and Strategic Deployment. *Baron Rodriguez, WestEd*

Developing Standards-Aligned Assessment Content with AI: Challenges and Early Lessons. *Sarah Quesen, WestEd*
Supporting Teachers in their AI Adoption for Instructional Improvement: Lessons from the AmpifyGAIN AI R&D Center. *Ann Edwards, WestEd*

Enhancing Cross-Sector Alignment with AI: Mapping Math Skills Across Education and Workforce. *Ann Edwards, WestEd*

Chair: *Antionette D. Stroter, Liberty University*

Discussant: *Jodi Davenport, WestEd*

79.030. Evaluating the Impact of Community Schooling: Comparing Methodologies and Findings Across States.

Division H - Research, Evaluation and Assessment in Schools; Symposium
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 7th Floor,
Hollywood Ballroom I; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Community Schools Impact on Student Outcomes: Evidence from California. *Walker A. Swain, LPI; Cassandra Rubinstein, Learning Policy Institute; Melanie Leung-Gagné, Learning Policy Institute; Anna Maier, Learning Policy Institute*

A Mixed-Methods Implementation and Impact Study of the Los Angeles Community Schools Initiative. *Lauren Covelli, RAND Corporation; Isaac Opper, RAND Corporation; Sabrina Lee; Susannah Faxon-Mills, RAND Corporation*

Understanding the impact of the statewide initiative for community schools in Maryland. *Jessica Shiller, Towson*

University; Rachel E. Durham, Notre Dame of Maryland University; Claudia L. Galindo, University of Maryland; Janae McDowell, Towson University

Using Quasi-Experimental Methods to Measure the Long-Term Academic Impacts of Community School Initiatives.

Kathleen Provinzano, Binghamton University - SUNY; Toni A. May, Binghamton University - SUNY; Naorah Rimkunas, Binghamton University - SUNY

Effectiveness Analyses Associated with the Chicago Community Schools Initiative. Neil Naftzger, American Institutes for Research; Dominique Bradley, American Institutes for Research

Community Schools Initial Impact on Student Attendance and the Importance of Student Engagement and Whole-child Supports. Nadia M. Sabat Bass, University of California - Los Angeles

Chairs: Karen Hunter Quartz, University of California - Los Angeles; Dandan Yang, University of California - Los Angeles

Discussant: Jordan Rickles, University of California - Los Angeles

79.031. Career Development in the Professions: Mentorship, Training, and Transformative Learning. Division I - Education in the Professions; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Atrium II; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Exploring Frequency of Mentorship Using Multisite Common Data from National Research Mentoring Network Studies. So Hee Hyun, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Abhijnya Menakur, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Christine Pfund, University of Wisconsin - Madison

Impact of a Grant Writing Workshop on Grantsmanship Confidence on Postdocs: A Mixed Methods Approach. Robyn Pennella, St. Jude Children's Research Hospital; Eric Rivera-Peraza, St. Jude Children's Research Hospital; Katherine Ayers, St. Jude Children's Research Hospital; Sally McIver, St. Jude Children's Research Hospital; Laura Wilt, St. Jude Children's Research Hospital

Investigating Participation in and Perceived Usefulness of Activities Provided by Biomedical Postdoctoral Training Programs. Inah Ko, University of Michigan; Jessy Martinez, University of Michigan; Tina Creguer, University of Michigan; Jessica Schwartz, University of Michigan

Transformative Field Education Through Collaboration: A Case Study of Freirean Social Work Pedagogy. Kendra Alexander, North Carolina A&T State University; Jeneya McLean, North Carolina A&T State University; Anthony Freeman, Guilford County School System; Torree Theodore, North Carolina A&T State University; Alyssa Najib, North Carolina A&T State University; Kaiya Whitehurst, North Carolina A&T State University; Jada Richardson, North Carolina A&T State University

Chair: Kyoungjin Jang-Tucci, University of Wisconsin - Madison

Discussant: Huiju Carrie Chen, Kaiser Permanente Bernard J. Tyson School of Medicine

79.032. Advancing Higher Education: International Perspectives. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum G; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Academic and Cultural Interactions with Mentors/Advisors: International Graduate Students in U.S. STEM Programs. Scott M Myers, Montana State University; Carrie B. Myers, Montana State University

Internationalization of Higher Education in the Global South: Voices from Students in International Programs. Neng Priyanti, University of Houston; Summer Danielle Crawley, University of Houston

Living in Between: Navigating Temporal, Spatial, and Legal Precarity as International Students. Shuang Fu, New York University

Living on the Edge: A Critical Review of Visa Insecurity, Institutional (Un)safety, and Mental Health Challenges of International Students in U.S. Higher Education. John O. Ajamobe, Texas A&M University; Oluwafisayo Grace Ajamobe, University of Ibadan

Understanding the Mental Health and Coping Strategies of Chinese International Students in the U.S.: A Qualitative Study. Jing Su, University of California - Santa Barbara

79.033. Balancing Acts and Breaking Walls: Centering Equity Amid Organizational Change and Complexity. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum H; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Building and Boosting Capacity in Higher Education: Lessons Learned from Institutions Serving Diverse Student Populations. Naomi Stephen, University of California - Los Angeles; Krystle Cobian, University of California - Los Angeles; Ana L. Romero, University of California - Los Angeles; Sylvia Hurtado, University of California - Los Angeles

Pushing Boulders: Mapping Barriers to Conduct Equity-Informed Assessment. Beth Janetski, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Yi-Chin Wu, Georgia Institute of Technology; Mary K. Thompson, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Julene L Jones, University of Kentucky

Understanding the Balancing Act: Stability, Change, and Organizational Continuity in Higher Education. Jay R. Dee, University of Massachusetts - Boston; Cheryl Daly, Kittery and Marshwood School Districts; Anne M. DeFelippo, Salem State University

Racialized Sustainability: How Race and Power Shape the Institutionalization of STEM Intervention Programs. Edwin

J. Perez, University of Texas - El Paso

Chair: *Jimmy Aguilar, University of Southern California*

Discussant: *Deborah E. Southern, University of California - Los Angeles*

79.034. First-Generation College Students Perspectives: Adjusting to Campus, Financial Aid, College Access, and Belonging. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum F;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Culture Shock on Campus: Narratives of First-Generation Rural College Students Navigating Their Freshman Year. *Pietro Antonio Sasso, Delaware State University; Justin L. Alexander, Delaware State University; Chetanath Gautam, Delaware State University*

Investing in Uncertainty: Student Loans, Value Perception, and Financial Impact for First-Generation Students. *Angie L. Miller, Indiana University; Candace Marie Henry, University of South Florida; Matthew P. Ison, Western Michigan University*

Transitioning to Post-Secondary Education Through the Promise Scholars College Access Program for Low-Income, First-Generation Canadians. *Andrea Hill, Queen's University - Kingston; Alana C. Butler, Queen's University - Kingston*

Becoming Family: Alumni Perspectives on Belonging in a College Prep Program for First-Gen, Low-Income Students. *Bethany Monea, University of the District of Columbia; Mia Hines, George Mason University; Khaseem Davis, Georgetown University; Bailey Highsmith, George Mason University; Brian Staples, George Mason University*

Chair: *Collin Perryman, Arizona State University*

79.035. Elementary Pre-Service Teacher Education: Feedback, Futures, Technology, and Equity. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 8;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Designing Futures: Preservice Teachers Reimagining Inquiry for a New Vision of Elementary Education. *Matthew Odebiyi, Arizona State University*

Elementary Preservice Teachers' Understanding of Technology's Role in Equity Pedagogy. *Lauren Weisberg, University of Texas - Arlington; Christine Wusylko, Kennesaw State University; Blake Mickle Beckett, University of Florida*

Excavation, Emotionality, and Evasion: Examining Racial Literacy Development in Elementary Teacher Education. *Michael Young, Illinois State University*

Exploring Professionalism in Early Childhood Teacher Education: Insights from a Scoping Review. *Yue Qi, Pennsylvania State University*

Reflection of AI-generated lesson plans as dialogic work for preservice teachers. *Jessie M. Nixon, Weber State University; Katarina Anderson, Weber State University; Ryan F. Cain, Weber State University; Gisela Martiz, Utah State University*

Chair: *Rosie Ojeda, California Polytechnic State University - San Luis Obispo*

Discussant: *Arthi B. Rao, University of Illinois at Chicago*

79.036. Empowered Praxis: Centering Teacher Agency, Identities, and Knowledges. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 6;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Beyond Subversion: Latinx Literacy Leaders and the Emergence of a Praxis of Refusal. *Laura Keisler, California State University - Fullerton; Rosario M. Ordonez-Jasis, California State University - Fullerton; Madeleine Mejia, California State University - Fullerton*

Centering Community Voices to Empower Teachers as Catalysts for Social Justice. *Faiza Zafar, Rice University; Carolyn Nichol, Rice University; Christina Alston, University of Colorado - Boulder; Veronica Ajewole-Mwema, Texas Southern University; Ivy O. Poon, Texas Southern University; Kassie Thompson, Texas Southern University; Maria Mejia, Florida Atlantic University; Diego Lopez, Rice University; Mirna Mendoza Wilson, Rice University*

Cultivating the Educational Field: An Exploration of Indigenous Teachers' Conscientization Experiences in Taiwan. *Liang-Yu Ong, National Taiwan Normal University; Hsiao-Lan Chen, National Taiwan Normal University*

Fairness Reimagined: Teacher Agency in L2 Writing Assessment in the Age of AI. *Sitong Wang, McGill University*

Transnational Praxis in Confronting Linguistic Racism in English Language Teacher Education. *Jenifer Crawford, University of Southern California; Patricia Nuñez-Mercado, Universidad Veracruzana; Elida Sanchez-Cruz, Universidad Veracruzana*

Chair: *Lybrya Kebreab, California State University - Pomona*

Discussant: *Ilene Ivins, Alder Graduate School of Education*

79.037. Grief as a Portal to the Past, Present, and Future: Narratives of Educators of Color. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 7;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

'I Was Never Told About the Sorrow': A Critical Narrative on Embracing Grief as a Practice for Healing and Possibility. *Sara Jasmin Diaz-Montejano, University of California - Los Angeles*

Understanding Grief as an Ethnic Studies Praxis. *Lauren Arzaga Daus, University of California - Los Angeles*
Teaching Through Grief: Reflections on Masculinity for Men of Color. *JC Lugo, California State University - Northridge*
Chair: *Stephanie Cariaga, California State University - Dominguez Hills*
Discussant: *Sharim Hannegan-Martinez, University of Michigan*

79.038. Teacher Educator Identity and Ideation: Reimagining the Discourse. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 9; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Teacher Educator Identity: An Elusive Construct. *Jason K. Ritter, Duquesne University; Reva Mathieu-Sher, Duquesne University*

Teaching Teachers for Deeper Learning: How Teacher Educators Support Preservice Teachers in Learning to Teach for Deeper Learning. *Matthew D. Bennett, University of California - Santa Barbara; Oishee Mujtaba, University of California - Santa Barbara; Jing Su, University of California - Santa Barbara; Daniel Rafael Santana, University of California - Santa Barbara; Yvette Doss, University of California - Santa Barbara; Ying Gao, University of California - Santa Barbara; Danielle B. Harlow, University of California - Santa Barbara; Mian Wang, University of California - Santa Barbara*

Wonder-Full Education: A Collaborative Discourse on Wonder. *Son T. H. Pham, Nha Viet Institute; Jean Kiekel, University of St. Thomas; Carley Fisher-Maltese, George Mason University; Sarah Gailey, Weber State University*

Chair: *Keisha McIntosh Allen, University of Maryland*

Discussant: *Hazel Vega, Clemson University*

79.039. Controversial Issues Policies, Power, and Practices: How Educators Navigate Hostile and Divisive Political Climates. Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Symposium

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 10; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Policy Ambiguity, Erasure, and Discrimination: Why Gender-Inclusive Educational Leadership is Imperative During Authoritarian Drift. *Mollie McQuillan, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Benjamin Lebovitz, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Madelaine Adelman, Arizona State University; Cris Mayo, University of Vermont; Rin Xie, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

"It Creates an Expectation That Everybody's Story is Worth Being Told:" Librarians Countering Censorship Policies. *Madelaine Adelman, Arizona State University; Daniel D. Liou, Arizona State University; Courtney Langerud, Arizona State University*

What is Taught and What is Learned: Lessons from an Antiracist Middle School. *Alexandra J. Freidus, University of Connecticut*

"Of the meaning of progress": School Choice, Black Educators, and White Epistemological Capture during Crisis. *Kevin Lawrence Henry, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Understanding Youth of Color's Political Education and Activism Amid Polarizing Times. *Gabriel Rodriguez, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Chair: *Mollie McQuillan, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Discussant: *Luis A Rodriguez, New York University*

79.040. Innovations in Leadership Evaluation: Policy, Practice, and Emerging Technologies. Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 1; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Determining "Fit": Principal and HR Administrator Perspectives on Selecting First-Time Assistant Principals. *Kimberly Jamison, University of North Carolina - Wilmington; Helen Gross, Onslow County Schools*

Leveraging Large Language Models (LLMs) to Measure Aspiring School Leaders' Capacities. *Jacob Mitchell Rubin, Vanderbilt University; Jason A. Grissom, Vanderbilt University*

Chair: *Kimberly Jamison, University of North Carolina - Wilmington*

Discussant: *Zhaochen Gu, University of Illinois at Chicago*

SIG Sessions

79.041. Immersive Technologies in Education: Enhancing Learning Through VR, AR, and Robotics. SIG-Advanced Technologies for Learning; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Santa Barbara A; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Impact of Augmented Reality-Enhanced Biological Taxonomy Instruction on Student Achievement and Science Motivation. *Anthony Ilobinso, Purdue University; Victoria Lynn Lowell, Purdue University; Stuart K. White, Purdue University; Kevin Jones, Krueger Middle School, Middle school in Michigan City, Indiana*

Tutor-Learner Physiological Synchrony & Rapport in Cross-Reality Interactions. *Michelle Lui, University of Toronto; Mengqiu Cheng, University of Toronto - OISE; Jiaying Yu, University of Toronto - OISE; Martha Mullally, Carleton University*

Dimensionality and Dynamicity Matter in Geometry Learning: Comparing Augmented Reality, Tablets, Manipulatives, and Diagrams. *Julianna Washington-Henderson, Southern Methodist University; Candace A. Walkington, Southern*

Methodist University

The Impact of Interactive Digital Storytelling Robots on Student Motivation through Self-Determination Theory. *Ka Yan Fung, The Education University of Hong Kong; Yuxing Tao, The Education University of Hong Kong; Tze Leung Lui, The Education University of Hong Kong; Kuen Fung Kenneth Sin, The Education University of Hong Kong*

Confidence, Content, and Careers: Evaluating a VR-Based Instructional Approach in Microelectronics. *Rob Moore, University of Florida; Carl Westine, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Sophia Soomin Lee, University of Florida; Hyo Kang, University of Florida*

Discussant: *Hongming Li, University of Florida*

79.042. Transformative Visions for Arts Education. SIG-Arts and Learning; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Georgia I;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Aesthetic Praxis as Counter-History: Black Women Artists Refiguring Curriculum. *Jacqueline Cofield, Hunter College - CUNY*

Just Crushing: A Demolition Derby. *Allison V. Rowe, University of Iowa; Maia G. Sheppard, University of Iowa; Nancy Nowacek, Stevens Institute of Technology; Darrell Currington, University of Iowa*

Rethinking Time, Space, and Relationality: Disability-Centered Pedagogies in Art Learning. *Min Gu, California State University - Long Beach*

“Keep These Histories Alive!”: Harnessing Socially Conscious Art to Reimagine Ethnic Studies. *Clarence V. Walker, University of South Florida*

Chair: *Mindy Roberta Carter, McGill University*

Discussant: *Ambika Gopal Raj, California State University - Los Angeles*

79.043. Arts based educational research and critical care. SIG-Arts-Based Educational Research; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 504;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Artistic Elicitations: An Arts-Based Method Centered on Power and Care. *Jesenia Rosales, Oregon State University*

Arts for Joy’s Sake? An Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis of Arts Education in China’s Secondary Schools. *Ruini Huang, Ghent University; Yuxin Cao, Tsinghua University; Kris Rutten, Universiteit Gent*

Artist-Educator Identity: Critical Formation and Visual Narrative in Preservice Art Teachers. *Nora E. Rodriguez, University of Texas - San Antonio*

Chair: *Khalilah Odessa Ali, Spelman College*

Discussant: *Frances C. Furlong, College of William & Mary*

79.044. Reframing Research, Identity, and Belonging in Global

Higher Education for Asian International Students. SIG-Asian Americans and Pacific Islanders in Education and Research; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 501B;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Linkages of Temporality, Spatiality, and Racial Positioning of Asian International Students in the U.S. *Christina W. Yao, University of South Carolina*

Asian International Students’ Racial-Ethnic Identity in a Post-Pandemic Era: A Longitudinal Mixed-Methods Study. *Jia Zheng, University of Massachusetts - Amherst; Shinji Katsumoto, University of Southern Mississippi*

Exploring Racial Literacy among Chinese International Students in U.S. Higher Education. *Jing Yu, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Unsettling Measurement Validity: A Critical Mixed Methods Study with Asian International Students. *HyeJin Tina Yeo, University of California - Los Angeles*

Chair: *Xinhang Hermione Hu, University of Maryland*

Discussant: *Kristyn Lue, University of Southern California*

79.045. Navigating Taiwan’s Bilingual Education Reform and Sustainability Movement through a Glocalization Lens. SIG-Bilingual Education Research; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304B;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Fostering Intercultural Competence through Translanguaging: A Bilingual Program Connecting Taiwanese and Taiwanese American Youth. *Ming-Hsuan Wu, Adelphi University*

Glocalized Professional Development for Sustainable Bilingual Education in Taiwan. *Rae Ping Lin, National Taiwan Ocean University; Wenli Tsou, National Cheng Kung University*

Translanguaging in Action: A Sustainable Model for the Expanding Circle. *Ivy Haoyin Hsieh, National Dong Hwa University*

Chair: *Ming-Hsuan Wu, Adelphi University*

Discussant: *Genevieve Leung, University of San Francisco*

79.046. Intensive Parenting Across Cultures: Global Varieties in Mobilizing Cultural Capital. SIG-Bourdieu in Educational Research; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304C;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

The Privileged Path: Live-in-Home Tutors and Cultural Capital Transmission in Affluent Chinese Families. *Lu Liu, University of Liverpool; Lixin Ren, Xi'an Jiaotong-Liverpool University*

Distinction Reconfigured: Habitual Privilege, Cultural Capital, and the Performance of Middle-Class Parenting in Germany. *Frederick de Moll, Bielefeld University; Janice Aurini, University of Waterloo*

Learning in the community: Middle-class immigrant parent engagement and devaluation of cultural capital in schools.

Max Antony-Newman, University of Glasgow

Schools, capital, and the perpetuation of advantage: the case of return migrant families in India. *Adrienne L. Atterberry, University of Massachusetts - Lowell*

Chairs: *Frederick de Moll, Bielefeld University; Guanglun Michael Mu, University of South Australia*

Discussant: *Erin McNamara Horvat, Drexel University*

79.047. Restorative Justice, Black Geographies, and Voice: Reframing School Discipline as a Fight for Human Rights. SIG-Classroom Management; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Georgia II; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

A Systematic Literature Review of Conceptions, Implementation, and Evaluation of Restorative Practices in U.S. K-12 Schools. *Laura Fitz Parks, Fort Lewis College*

Managing Students and Space: A review of 21st-century classroom management interventions. *Janaya Little, University of Pennsylvania*

Lost learning: prevalence, inequalities and outcomes of internal exclusion in mainstream secondary schools. *Neil Humphrey, University of Manchester*

“If I’m a Good Citizen of My Classroom, I Get a Reward for It”. *Abigail Stebbins, The Ohio State University*

Centering Student Perspectives in Restorative Practices. *Laura Fitz Parks, Fort Lewis College*

Discussant: *Dorothy E. Hines, University of Kansas*

79.048. Doing Critical Quantitative Research: Methodological Commitments to Equity and Justice. SIG-Critical Quantitative Methodologies; Symposium
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Echo Park; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

A Critical Re-Examination of Fairness on Massachusetts’s High-Stakes Assessment and Graduation. *John Wang, University of Virginia; Wendy Castillo, Montclair State University*

Critical Quantitative Scholarship: Learning from Complex Interactions through a Person-Oriented Lens. *Hyun Kyoung Ro, Korea University; Bora Lee, Korea University*

Critical Possibilities: Interdisciplinary Recommendations on Using Secondary Data in Education for Social Justice. *Rachel L. Renbarger, FHI 360*

From Doing to Publishing QuantCrit: Perspectives on Peer Review Standards for Intersectionality and Quantitative Research. *Frank Fernandez, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Chair: *Frank Fernandez, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Discussant: *Hyun Kyoung Ro, Korea University*

79.049. Historicizing University-Community Links at 30: Proleptic Learnings in Resistance, Responsiveness, and Reimagining Education. SIG-Cultural-Historical Research
Cosponsored with Spotlight on Los Angeles and the Region; Symposium
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Santa Barbara C; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Historicizing UC Links: Sustaining Resistance and Responsiveness in University-Community Partnerships.

Eros Najera, University of California - Berkeley; Mara Welsh Mahmood, University of California - Berkeley; John Cano, University of California - Berkeley

Learning Lessons of Endurance: Long-Term Community-University Research Design. *Camille Campion, University of California - San Diego; Angela N. Booker, University of California - San Diego; Veverly Anderson, Town & Country Learning Center*

Sustaining University-Community Partnerships in Times of Change: Community-driven Goals Supporting Empowerment, Wellbeing, and Advocacy. *Sayra Martinez, La Colonia De Eden Garden Inc; Itzel Gonzalez Velazquez, University of California - San Diego; Amy Vathe Binliff, University of California - San Diego*

University-Community Partnership: Disrupting Institutional Culture and Honoring HSI Designation Through Community Servingness. *Monique Mercedes Estrada, UC Santa Barbara; Amanda Salcedo, University of California - Santa Barbara; Rebeca Mireles-Rios, University of California - Santa Barbara*

Chairs: *Mara Welsh Mahmood, University of California - Berkeley; John Cano, University of California - Berkeley*

Discussants: *Kris D. Gutiérrez, University of California - Berkeley; Shirin Vossoughi, Northwestern University*

79.050. Dewey in the Age of Artificial Intelligence; Or, On Being Human. SIG-Dewey Studies; Business Meeting
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 303A; 3:45-5:15pm

Chair: *Jiwon Kim, Monmouth University*

Speakers: *Guoping Zhao, Oklahoma State University; Huajun Zhang, Beijing Normal University; Leonard J. Waks, Qufu Normal University, Shandong China; Zongyi Deng, UCL Institute of Education, University College London*

Officers: *Jessica Heybach, Western Michigan University; Austin J. Pickup, Aurora University; James Yang, Beijing Normal-Hong Kong Baptist University; Rebecca Taylor, Teachers College, Columbia University*

79.051. Urban AI Unlocked: Transforming District Systems for Equitable AI Integration. SIG-Districts in Research & Reform; Symposium
Westin Bonaventure, Level 2, Beverly; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Co-Designing AI technologies with Youth: Design Choices that Reify Inequities or Envision Expansive Possibilities .
Thomas M. Philip, University of California - Berkeley;
Michael Alan Chang, Boston University

Procurement in the Age of Platforms: AI, Privatization, and Systemic Change in Urban School Districts. *Patricia Burch, University of Southern California; Junmin Byon, University of Southern California; Alvin Makori, University of Southern California; Shelby Leigh Smith, University of Southern California*

AI Early Adopter Districts: The Promises and Challenges of Using AI to Transform Education. *Robin Lake, Arizona State University; Steven Weiner, Arizona State University; Maddy Sims, Arizona State University; Bree Dusseault, Arizona State University*

Status Report on California Schools and Districts for AI in Schools: How Ready Are we? *Victor R. Lee, Stanford University*

Chair: *Stephen J. Aguilar, University of Southern California*

Discussants: *Patrick Gittisriboongul, Lynwood Unified School District; Jerry Almendarez, Santa Ana Unified School District; Niral Shah, University of Washington*

79.052. Supporting the ECE Workforce: Findings from Four System-Level Professional Development Initiatives. SIG-Early Education and Child Development; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 3; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Piloting a Collaborative Approach to Workforce Development in Early Childhood Special Education. *Jackie Robinson Brock, Virginia Commonwealth University; Jennifer LoCasale-Crouch, University of Virginia; Nora Bryant, Virginia Commonwealth University; Yuqi Zhang, Virginia Commonwealth University*

Impact of Higher Reimbursement Rates on Family Child Care Quality and Workforce Stability. *Sandra L. Soliday Hong, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Lindsay Gomes, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Kylie L. Garber, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*

Linguistically Responsive Professional Development: Offerings, Access, and Outcomes for a Multilingual ECE Workforce. *Yujin Lee, University of Massachusetts - Boston; Nicole Restrepo, University of Massachusetts - Boston; Anne Douglass, University of Massachusetts - Boston*

Examining Features and Outcomes of a Residency-Based Licensure Pathway for Early Childhood Educators. *Joanna Skourletos, Loyola University Chicago; Emma Gregory Casey, George Mason University; Kate Zinsser, University of Illinois at Chicago; Catherine M. Main, University of Illinois at Chicago; Timothy W. Curby, George Mason University; Natalie Vesga, University of Illinois at Chicago*

Chair: *Anne Douglass, University of Massachusetts - Boston*

Discussant: *Anne Douglass, University of Massachusetts - Boston*

79.053. Harnessing Waldorf for Arts-based Trauma Pedagogy Across Borders: Opportunities & Challenges. SIG-Elliott Eisner; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 306B; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Developmentally Appropriate Learning Supports in Crisis Contexts: Essence of Learning in a Pristina, Kosovo Classroom. *Beatrice Rutishauser, ReGeneration; shepha Vainstein, ReGeneration*

Overcoming Powerlessness -Building Shared Strength to Meet Shared Crisis - stART international in Crisis Zones. *Ida Oberman, Alanus University of Arts and Social Sciences; Barbara Schiller, stART Internationa E.V.*

When All Has Gone to Ash: Kindergarten Puppetry&Storytelling after LA Fires: Emergency-Pedagogy-Without-Borders, Team USA. *Rosa Balderrama, Pasadena Waldorf School; Ida Oberman, Alanus University of Arts and Social Sciences*

From Emergency to Trauma Work: Associação-da-Pedagogia-de-Emergência Partners With University-teacher-training after the Grande-do-Sul -floods, Brazil 2024. *Reinaldo Nascimento, Monte Azul; Ida Oberman, Alanus University of Arts and Social Sciences*

Why Am I Putting on These Pink Slippers? “Eurythmy” in Milwaukee’s Inner City Waldorf School. *Andre Spencer Anderson-Thompson, University of California - Davis*

Chair: *Jennifer Bartee, University of the District of Columbia*
Discussants: *Lynn Butler-Kisber, McGill University; Melanie Reiser, Association of Waldorf Schools of North America*

79.054. Faculty as Teacher-Scholars. SIG-Faculty Teaching, Evaluation, and Development; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 2; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

A Phenomenological Exploration of Faculty Integrating Durable Skills to Prepare Career-Ready Transfer Students. *Christopher Butcher, Eastern Kentucky University*

Beyond Disciplinary Boundaries: How Interdisciplinary Teaching Relates to Faculty Pedagogical Practices across Disciplinary Contexts. *Stephen Craig Hiller, Indiana University; Thomas F. Nelson Laird, Indiana University; Emily Braught, Indiana University; Kyle Beyersdorf, Indiana University Bloomington*

Predictors of Faculty’s Perceived Artificial Intelligence Integration into Teaching Practices in Higher Education: The Mediating Role of Anxiety About AI Use. *Richard Dickson Amoako, University of Tennessee; Jennifer A. Morrow, University of Tennessee; Louis Rocconi, University of Tennessee*

Teaching in the Age of AI: Empowering Educators Through Professional Development. *Xi Lin, East Carolina University;*

Kristen H. Gregory, East Carolina University; Kenneth J. Luterbach, East Carolina University; Todd Blake Finley, East Carolina University; Sarah Sconyers, East Carolina University

Does Adaptive Equity-Oriented Pedagogy Predict Student Achievement across Universities? *Andrew Estrada Phuong, University of California - San Diego; Fan Huang, University of California - San Diego; Judy Nguyen, Stanford University; Carolyn H. Hofstetter, University of California - San Diego; Bowen Wang-Kildegaard, University of California - Berkeley; Fabrizio Daniel Mejia, University of California - Berkeley; Stanley Lo, University of California - San Diego; Christopher Todd Hunn, University of California - Berkeley*

79.055. From Coordination to Collaboration: Looking Across Healthcare and Educational Contexts to Support Children with Disabilities. SIG-Family, School,

Community Partnerships; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum I; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Family Navigation for Children with Special Health Care Needs: A Scoping Review. *Randall Owen, University of Nevada - Reno; Lex Owen, University of Nevada - Reno; Ruby Batz, University of Nevada - Reno*

Centering Youth and Caregiver Priorities: Perspectives on School Roles in Supporting Behavioral Health Outcomes. *Jennifer Murphy, University of Texas - Arlington; Genevieve Graaf, University of Texas - Arlington*

Examining the Role of Individualized Education Plans in Adequate Care Coordination and Mental Health Services. *Genevieve Graaf, University of Texas - Arlington; Jennifer Murphy, University of Texas - Arlington; Ambra Green, University of Texas - Arlington; Lex Owen, University of Nevada - Reno*

Attitudes and Practices Within Family School Partnership That Contribute to Special Educator Wellbeing. *Alexandra Turner, University of Vermont; Shana J. Haines, University of Vermont; Emily West-Geary, University of Vermont; Jessica Strolin-Goltzman, University of Vermont; Cynthia Jane Herbert, University of Vermont*

Family-Educator Relationships' Effect on Special Educator Well-Being. *Shana J. Haines, University of Vermont; Melanie Levitt, UVA; Emily West-Geary, University of Vermont; Alexandra Turner, University of Vermont; Jessica Strolin-Goltzman, University of Vermont*

Chair: *Lex Owen, University of Nevada - Reno*

Discussant: *Genevieve Graaf, University of Texas - Arlington*

79.056. Networked Continuous Improvement at Scale: Research Findings and Reflections from the NSI Initiative. SIG-Improvement Science in Education; Symposium

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, San Gabriel A; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Introductory Presentation. Scaling Improvement to Better Serve Black, Latino, and Low-Income Students — An Overview of the Network for School Improvement (NSI). *Andrew Sokatch, Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation*

Evaluation of the Networks for School Improvement Initiative—Relationship Between Network Hub Strategies and Supports and School Implementation of CI Activities. *Michael S. Garet, American Institutes for Research; Matthew J. Farmer, American Institutes for Research; Ryan C. Eisner, American Institutes for Research; Stephani L. Wrabel, University of Southern California; Becki Herman, RAND Corporation; Susan Bush-Mecenas, RAND Corporation*

Evaluation of the Networks for School Improvement Initiative—Impacts on Student Outcomes Final Report. *Matthew Johnson, Mathematica Policy Research, Inc; Naihobe Gonzalez, Mathematica Policy Research, Inc; Jeffrey Max; Tareena Musaddiq, Mathematica Policy Research, Inc; Sophia Seifert, Mathematica Policy Research, Inc; Michelle Bennett, Mathematica Policy Research, Inc*

Contextualizing the Evaluations of the NSI Initiative: Perspectives on Hub Leadership in Educational Improvement Networks. *Donald J. Peurach, University of Michigan; Megan Duff, UNC Chapel Hill; Jennifer Zoltners Sherer, University of Pittsburgh; Chris Matthis, Partners for Network Improvement*

Chair: *Susan Bush-Mecenas, RAND Corporation*

Discussants: *Juli Coleman, CORE Districts; David H. Eddy-Spicer, University of Virginia*

79.057. Critical Theories of Children's Museums: Unforgetting Institutional Harms and Imagining Equitable Futures.

SIG-Informal Learning Environment Research; Symposium
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Santa Anita B; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Conceived, Imagined, Lived: Bringing a Theory of Racialized Spaces to the Children's Museum. *Tarah Connolly, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

The Racialized Organization: Children's Museums and the (Re)Production of Racial Inequity through Organizational Practices. *Ashlyn Salvage, University of Pittsburgh*

Beyond Museum Neutrality and Innocence: Toward a "not-so-perfect" Pedagogy of Implication. *Lisa Farley, York University; Debbie Sonu, Hunter College - CUNY; Sandra Chang-Kredl, Concordia University; Gillian Parekh, York University*

Chair: *Alecia Dawn Young, University of Pittsburgh*

Discussant: *Alecia Dawn Young, University of Pittsburgh*

79.058. Latiné Voices in Print: Recent Books on Latiné

Student Experiences and Educational Equity. SIG-Latina/o/x Research Issues; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Plaza II;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Operationalizing Success from Latiné Student Perspectives.
Nichole M. Garcia, Rutgers University
From Community College to Baccalaureate Degree Attainment.
Marissa Vasquez, San Diego State University; José Reyes Del Real Viramontes, University of California - Riverside
Interrogating Concepts, Theories, and Methodologies for Studying Latiné Students in Higher Education. *Cristobal Salinas Jr, Florida Atlantic University*
Latiné Students in Engineering. *Sarah Rodriguez, Virginia Tech*
The Role of Activism and Politics in Defending Public Education. *Nolan L. Cabrera, University of Arizona*
Chair: *Javier Ezekiel Ramirez, University of Texas at Austin*
Discussant: *Nancy Acevedo, California State University - San Bernardino*

79.059. Fighting for Culturally Responsive-Sustaining Schools Under a New Administration. SIG-Leadership for School Improvement; Symposium
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, San Fernando; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

The Teacher Leader Perspective: Teaching for Justice When Justice is Under Attack. *Nicole C. Wilson Steffes, University of Utah & Westminster University; Katie Nitka, Salt Lake City School District; Aurora Torrejon, Salt Lake City School District; Laura Cheney, University of Utah*
The Assistant Principal Perspective: Leadership Through Human Connection. *Brian A. Valentine, Fairfax County Public Schools*
The Superintendent Perspective: Leading for Multilingual Equity. *Sandra Montañez-Diodonet, Passaic Public Schools*
The Special Education Coordinator Perspective: Restoring Humanity in Special Education. *Kristin Vogel-Campbell, North Point Educational Service Center*
The Community Partner Perspective: Community as Culturally Responsive Curriculum. *Andre'a J. Dorsey, University of the Virgin Islands*
The University Researcher Perspective: Coalitions for Culturally Responsive Change. *Meredith Wronowski, University of Dayton; Wesley Henry, Sacred Heart University; Bryan A. VanGronigen, University of Delaware*
Chairs: *Kristy Cooper Stein, Michigan State University; Soon-young Oh, Michigan State University*
Discussant: *Terah T. Venzant Chambers, Michigan State University*

79.060. Critical Leadership Perspectives May Enable New, More Equitable Educational Futures. SIG-Leadership for Social Justice; Symposium

Westin Bonaventure, Level 2, Echo Park; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Colonization and Indigenous methodology. *Mere Berryman, University of Waikato; Robert B. Donmoyer, University of San Diego*
Democratic and inclusive school leadership. *Dilys Schoorman, Florida Atlantic University; Betty M. Merchant, University of Texas - San Antonio; Olof CA Johansson, Umeå universitet*
Leading for Equity, Inclusion, and Human Rights. *Margaret Grogan, Chapman University; Steve Sider, Wilfrid Laurier University; Jhonel Morvan, CSCNO - Conseil scolaire catholique du Nouvel-Ontario*
Using a Critical Lens. *Zeus Leonardo, University of California - Berkeley; Jonathan Desmon Russell Pérez, The School of The New York Times; Khalid Husny Arar, Texas State University*
Chair: *Carolyn M. Shields, Wayne State University*
Discussant: *Carolyn M. Shields, Wayne State University*

79.061. Selecting and Teaching with Diverse Books in Challenging Times: Learning from Research with Pre-Service Teachers, Teachers, and Teacher Educators. SIG-Literature; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Los Cerritos; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Curating for Change: A Four-Year Study of Early Childhood Educators' Picturebook Selection Practices. *Mengying Xue, University of Missouri; Maile Newberry-Wortham, University of Missouri; Angie Zapata, University of Missouri; Candace R. Kuby, University of Missouri; Cassidy Beach, University of Missouri*
"We Had No Issues with this Book": Affordances and Challenges in Critically Discussing Justice-Oriented Picturebooks. *Erin K. Hogan, University of Louisville; James S. Chisholm, University of Louisville; Amy Eisenback, University of Louisville*
A Wide Range: Approaches to Integrating Diverse Literature in Secondary ELA Classrooms. *Arianna Banack, University of South Florida; Rosa Nam, Colorado State University*
From Tension to Reimagination: Preservice Teachers Analyze Diverse Children's Literature in a Shifting Educational Climate. *Jennifer Anne McCreight, Kent State University; Abbey Galeza, Kent State University*
Chair: *Selena E Van Horn, California State University - Fresno*
Discussant: *Kimberly McDavid Schmidt, University of Denver*

79.062. To Resist: Examining a District-Wide Implementation of a Middle School Anti-Bias Curriculum in the Current Socio-Political Climate. SIG-Middle-Level Education Research; Symposium
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Los Feliz; 3:45-5:15pm
Participants:

Historical Context and Contemporary Antiracist Education in Albemarle County Public Schools. *Neeley Minton, Albemarle County Public Schools*

“Im so worried...” Examining Middle School Teachers Experiences Teaching an Anti-Bias Curriculum Under New Federal Guidelines”. *Johari Harris, Kennesaw State University*

Chair: *Kristie W. Smith, Kennesaw State University*

Discussant: *Melissa Hairston, Albermarle County Public Schools*

79.063. Examining the Impact of Montessori Instructional Experiences. SIG-Montessori Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum J; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Chronic HPA Axis Activity in Grades 1-8 in Public Montessori and Conventional Schools. *Amanda M. Dettmer, Yale University; Angeline S. Lillard, University of Virginia; Xin Tong, University of Virginia*

Public Montessori Preschool’s Impact on Achievement Gaps in Kindergarten. *Emily Daggett, University of Virginia; Angeline S. Lillard, University of Virginia; David Loeb, University of Pennsylvania; Xin Tong, University of Virginia; Star Markowitz, University of Virginia*

Innovative Coaching and Its Impact on Instructional Practices. *Barbara S. Rieckhoff, DePaul University; Sharon J. Damore, DePaul University; Courtney McWilliams, University of Wisconsin River Falls*

Chair: *Brooke Culclasure, Furman University*

79.064. Deeper Insights Through NAEP Innovation. SIG-NAEP Studies; Paper Session

InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 6th Floor, Broadway; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Applying Human Opportunity Index to NAEP HSTS: Understanding Access to Advanced Coursework for All Students. *Judy H. Tang, Westat; Laura Coward Egan, Westat*

The Need for NAEP to Measure Bullying: Is a Single Item Enough? *Anthony Betancourt, University of Scranton*

Beyond the Score: Using Digital NAEP Math Assessment Data to Support Teachers. *Hongwen Guo, Educational Testing Service; Matthew S. Johnson, Educational Testing Service; Jeremy Lee, ETS; Luis Enrique Saldivia, ETS; Michelle Worthington, ETS; Kadriye Ercikan, Educational Testing Service*

Tracking Cross-State Gender Gap Trajectory in NAEP Assessments with Dynamic Time Warping Methods. *Qiwei He, Georgetown University*

79.065. Teachers and teacher education in problem and project based learning environments. SIG-Problem-Based and Project-Based Learning; Paper Session

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Santa Anita C; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Challenges in PBL Teaching: Based on Analysis of Teachers' Classroom Videos and Interviews. *Jing Lin, Beijing Normal University*

Enhancing Strategic Thinking and Negotiation Skills through Problem-Based Learning in International Studies. *Maria Kolovou, University of Miami; Dina Moulioukova, University of Miami*

Teacher Commitments and Instructional Variation in Project-Based Learning in a Multilingual International School. *Christina Krist, Stanford University; Shuai Xu, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Bee U. Butler, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Investigating the Effect of Case and Contextual Features on Preservice Teachers’ Case-Scenario Response Quality. *Petra Hellene Cadwell-Cowan, Washington State University; Kira J. Carbonneau, Washington State University; Chad M. Gotch, Washington State University; Shenghai Dai, Washington State University; Yuliya Ardashova, Washington State University - Tri Cities; Sarah L. Newcomer, Washington State University - Tri-Cities*

A Systematic Review of Formative Assessment Methods in Project-Based and Problem-Based Learning. *Hui Zhong, The College of William & Mary; Caroline Nicole Utne Finchum, College of William & Mary*

Chair: *Jing Lin, Beijing Normal University*

79.066. Qualitative Research SIG Closed Mentoring Session.

SIG-Qualitative Research; Paper Session
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Wilshire Grand Ballroom I; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Qualitative Research SIG Closed Mentoring Session #1. *Pengfei Zhao, McGill University*

Qualitative Research SIG Closed Mentoring Session #2. *Shena Sanchez, University of Alabama*

Qualitative Research SIG Closed Mentoring Session #3. *Meagan Call-Cummings, Johns Hopkins University*

Chairs: *Pengfei Zhao, McGill University; Susan Ophelia Cannon, University of Georgia; Lindsay Jarratt, University of Iowa; Lorien S. Jordan, University of South Florida; Alycia M. Elfreich, Montana State University; Carlson Coogler, Baylor University; Jason Laker, San José State University; Francheska Starks, University of Tennessee*

Discussants: *Enkhchimeg Sharav, Montana State University; Zijun Wu, university of utah; Sarah Ann Harris, Baylor University; Amanda Shear, University of Pennsylvania; Gabriela López, Stanford University; Kyle P. Smith, University of Michigan; Abayomi Israel Olaofe, Lagos State University, Ojo, Lagos State; Jennifer Sutcliffe, Michigan State University; Jessica Marie Yauney, Stanford University; Maria S. Guarino, Teachers College, Columbia University;*

Chris Cyan Divens; Zia Pochkhanawala, Baylor University; Jacqueline White, Texas A&M University; Bhushan Dahal, Florida State University; Zander Nowell, University of Colorado - Boulder; Daria Smirnova, University of South Florida; Arisandy Johnson, Arizona State University; Pinyi Wang, University of Florida; Asia Trammell, University of Redlands; Mariane de Araujo Batista-McCulloch, University of Minnesota; Amanda Laker, Teachers College, Columbia University; Jonathan M. Coker, Coastal Carolina University; Alexandra Panos, University of South Florida; Alycia M. Elfreich, Montana State University; Jennifer R. Esposito, Georgia State University; Marcus B. Weaver-Hightower, Virginia Tech; Jessica Van Cleave, Gardner-Webb University; Mirka E. Koro, Arizona State University; Constance Steinkuehler Squire, University of California - Irvine; Kakali Bhattacharya, University of Florida; Reka C. Barton, University of Maryland; Meseret F. Hailu, University of Georgia; Tracey Terece Flores, University of Texas at Austin; Roderick L. Carey, University of Delaware; Jeong-Eun Rhee, Long Island University - C.W. Post Campus; Stephanie Anne Shelton, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Jennifer R. Wolgemuth, University of South Florida; Kelly W. Guyotte, University of Alabama; Jeong-Hee Kim, Texas Tech University

79.067. Straight Talk: Natural Language Processing Approaches to Characterizing Student Opportunities to Learn in Mathematics. SIG-Research in Mathematics Education; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum A; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Detecting Student Idea Attribution: A Computational Approach to Characterizing Equitable Teaching Practice. Jackie Ramos Draper, HARVARD GRAD SCHOOL OF ED; Jeannette Garcia Coppersmith, Harvard University; Bailey Buchanan, Harvard University; Heather C. Hill, Harvard University

Mapping Multilingual Students' Mathematical Vocabulary Usage, Cognitive Engagement, and Belonging in Middle-Grades Math Classrooms. Bailey Buchanan, Harvard University; Jeannette Garcia Coppersmith, Harvard University

Teachers' Language in Mathematics: A Question of Student Diversity. Hannah Kleen, DIPF | Leibniz Institute for Research and Information in Education; Katharina Wehking, University of Osnabrück; Patrick Schreyer, University of Kassel; Helene Zeeb, University of Erfurt
¿Por Qué No Los Dos? Multilingual Spanish Speaking Student Practices in Mathematics Classrooms. Liliana Santos-Deonizio, Stanford University; Jim Malamut, Stanford University

Chairs: Jeannette Garcia Coppersmith, Harvard University; Jim Malamut, Stanford University

Discussant: Jonee Wilson, University of Virginia

79.068. AI as a Co-Pilot in Science Education: Reimagining Instructional Practice. SIG-Science Teaching and Learning; Structured Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 515B; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

1. Realizing the Potential of Automatically Scored Three-Dimensional Assessment (Poster 1). Joseph S. Krajcik, Michigan State University; Namsoo Shin, Michigan State University; Ehsan Latif, University of Georgia; Xiaoming Zhai, University of Georgia; Christopher J. Harris, WestEd; David McKinney, WestEd
2. Integrating Artificial Intelligence with Augmented Reality for Scientific Modeling (Poster 2). Bryan A. Brown, Stanford University; Alan Cheng, Stanford University; Lisa Teresa Archuleta, Stanford University; Elizabeth Childs, Stanford University; Roy D. Pea, Stanford University; Laurence Tan, University of California - Los Angeles
3. Training Culturally Relevant AI Models for Science Instruction (Poster 3). Bryan A. Brown, Stanford University; Alan Cheng, Stanford University; Lisa Teresa Archuleta, Stanford University; Elizabeth Childs, Stanford University; Roy D. Pea, Stanford University; Laurence Tan, University of California - Los Angeles
4. Integrating AI into Classroom Discussion Routines: Helping students express their science thinking (Poster 4). Allison Bradford, University of California - Berkeley; Libby F. Gerard, University of California - Berkeley; Marcia Linn, University of California - Berkeley
5. AI-Supported Feedback to Scaffold Scientific Argumentation (Poster 5). Lei Liu, Educational Testing Service; Field Watts, Educational Testing Service; Yi Song, Educational Testing Service; Euvelisse Jusino-Del Valle, Educational Testing Service; Ninghao Liu, University of Georgia; Xiaoming Zhai, University of Georgia
6. Co-Design at the Human-AI Frontier: Secondary Science Educators' Practices and Perspectives on Generative Molecular Design (Poster 6). Kent J. Crippen, University of Florida; Minji Yun, University of Florida; Charles Xie, Institute for Future Intelligence; Annie Levendusky, University of Florida; Dylan Bulseco, Institute for Future Intelligence
7. Human Experts' Evaluation of Generative AI's Potential to Contextualize STEAM Education in the Global South (Poster 7). Matthew Nyaaba, University of Georgia; Macharious Nabang, Bagabaga College of Education; Patrick Kyeremeh, St. Joseph's College of Education; Xiaoming Zhai, University of Georgia; Collins Owusu-Fordjour, University of Education - Winneba; Ibrahim Nantomah, University for Development Studies
8. Culturally Responsive and Sustaining Teaching Practices using Artificial Intelligence (Poster 8). Melinda Crystal

Lopez, University of Colorado - Boulder

Chairs: Xiaoming Zhai, University of Georgia; Bryan A. Brown, Stanford University

Discussant: James W. Pellegrino, University of Illinois at Chicago

79.069. Subversive Pedagogies and Critical Special Education in an Era of Surveillance and Silencing. SIG-Special and Inclusive Education Research; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum C; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Imagining Inclusive Futures in Teacher Education Through Program Redesign. *Keishana L. Barnes, University of Memphis; William C. Hunter, University of Memphis*

“Difficult Days Ahead”: An Autoethnography of an Inaugural Critical Special Education Course amidst Controversial Topic Laws. *Kayla Larkin, University of Memphis; Keishana L. Barnes, University of Memphis; William C. Hunter, University of Memphis; LaSheba Hilliard, University of Memphis; Suman Rath, Montclair State University*

Towards Critically Inclusive Teacher Education: Fostering Critical Perspectives of Dis/ability amongst Preservice Teachers. *Kayla Larkin, University of Memphis; Vanessa Lopez, University of Miami*

Designing a Critical Special Education Syllabus Amid Divisive Concept Laws: An Autoethnographic Account in an Undergraduate Teacher Education Program. *Suman Rath, Montclair State University*

Chair: *Elizabeth Holliday Morgan, Morgan State University*

Discussant: *William C. Hunter, University of Memphis*

79.070. Structures and Supports for Imagining Futures in Teacher Research. SIG-Teacher as Researcher; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum B; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Structures and Supports: The AERA TAR SIG. *Kevin Cataldo, Newark Board of Education/Montclair State University*

Structures and Supports: The National Writing Project. *Tanya Baker, National Writing Project*

Structures and Supports: The Multilingual Inquiry Collaborative. *Jane Charlotte Weiss, Stanford University*

Chair: *Mary Klehr, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Discussant: *Kierstin M. Giunco, University of Cincinnati*

79.071. Research on teaching and learning in educational psychology: The role of motivation. SIG-Teaching Educational Psychology; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, La Cienega; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Analyzing Service-learning Experiences in an Educational Psychology Course Using a Self-determination Theoretical

Framework. *Jill D. Salisbury-Glennon, Auburn University; Paris S. Strom, Auburn University; Amber Johnson, Auburn University; Kendrick Wallace, Auburn University*
Can Teacher Efficacy Improve Student Academic Efficacy and Their Psychological Needs? The Role of Need-Supportive Teaching. *Yu Wu, University of Memphis; Qiang Andy Cheng, University of Mississippi; Yonghong Jade Xu, University of Memphis*

How Can We Teach Development, Learning Theories, Motivation, and Assessment to Better Prepare Future Educators? *Wonjoon Cha, The Ohio State University; Arianna Henning, The Ohio State University; Eric M. Anderman, The Ohio State University*

Relationships Between Motivational Climate and Course Ratings in an Educational Psychology Course Over Time. *Saylor Bane, Virginia Tech; Brett D. Jones, Virginia Tech; Zeynep Ambarkutuk, Virginia Tech; Hande Fenerci, Virginia Tech*

Chair: *Susanne Narciss, Technische Universitaet Dresden*

Discussant: *Anna C. Brady, Georgia Southern University*

Division and SIG Roundtables

79.072. AERA Roundtable Session Saturday 3:45 pm;
Roundtable Session

79.072-1. Educational Leadership in Rural and Remote Communities (Table 1). Division A - Administration;
Roundtable Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Unforgetting Marginalization, Imagining Just Futures: Rural Technology and Leadership. *Hosna khorsandi, University of Denver; Rezvan Khorsandi; Tiyanjane Mwenda Dzilankhulani, University of Denver*

Leading a Successful and Flourishing Australian Rural School. *Christopher Hudson, Westbourne Grammar School; David M. Gurr, University of Melbourne*

Understanding the Urban-Rural Education Divide in China: A Knowledge Systems and Leadership Perspective. *Mengying Cao, The George Washington University*

Quilted Narratives: Exploring Rural Appalachian Women's Leadership Through Story and Identity. *Leanna Rippey, Virginia Tech; Charles L. Lowery, Virginia Tech*

Chair: *Kelly S. Hall, Texas A&M University - Kingsville*

79.072-2. Equity and Social Justice Leadership Among Backlash Against DEI (Table 2). Division A - Administration; Roundtable Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Speaking from the Heart, Listening from the Heart: Toward an Emergent Theory of Restorative Leadership. *Leah Ann Raphael, University of California - Los Angeles; Tonikiaa Orange, University of California - Los Angeles; Tarik Smith, University of California - Los Angeles*

Increasingly Diverse Schools: Coming from Our Histories toward Leading in a Time of DEI Backlash. *Martin Scanlan, Boston College; George Theoharis, Syracuse University*

Reimagining Radical Community Engagement through Culturally Responsive School Leadership: A Case Study of Award-Winning Principals. *Brian C. Vedder, University of Denver; Amanda B Roberts, University of Denver; Jayson W. Richardson, College of William & Mary; Erin Anderson, University of Denver; William L. Sterrett, Baylor University*

Beyond the Office: Othermothering as Praxis for Black Women Principals. *Jéri L. Ogden, Marymount University*

Chair: *Lauren P. Bailes, University of Delaware*

79.072-3. Equity Leadership: Equity Networks and Women Leaders of Color (Table 3). Division A - Administration; Roundtable Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Advancing Intersectional Justice in Higher Education: Chicana/Latina Change Agents Nurturing Transformative Ruptures. *Brianna R. Ramirez, Glendale Community College; Maria Anzaldo, California State Polytechnic University - Pomona; Nataly De La Pena, California State University; Ana Alejandra Zambrano, California Polytechnic State University - Pomona*

Black Women Superintendents: The Most Disrespected Educator in America. *Gregory C. Hutchings, Howard University; Danita Y. Ishibashi, The College of New Jersey*
'Is there some sort of a network that exists?': Examining equity director professional learning in a regional equity network. *Andrew Matschiner, Chapman University; Ishmael Miller, Arizona State University*

Unforgetting Culturally Responsive K-12 Leadership Preparation in an Anti-DEI Era: A Narrative Self-Study. *John Pascarella, University of Southern California*

Chair: *Catherine L. Zhang, University of Pennsylvania*

79.072-4. Expanding the Horizons of Leadership Development: Intercultural, Contextual, and Practice-Based Insights (Table 4). Division A - Administration; Roundtable Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Centering on the Peripheral: Reimagining Administrator Support Through the Voices and Networks of Teacher Leaders. *Timothy Aberle, Montclair State University; John O'Meara, Montclair State University; Shanna Dawn*

Anderson, Montclair State University; Mika Munakata, Montclair State University; Emily J. Klein, Montclair State University; Monica Taylor, Montclair State University
Exploring The Impact Of Instructional Coaching Within Principal Preparation On Student Achievement. *Sarah De La Garza, Texas Tech University; Shyneil Porter-Quigley, Texas Tech University; Lyndah Naswa Wasike, Texas Tech University; E. Vanessa de Leon, Texas Tech University; Fernando Valle, Texas Tech University; Irma Laura Almager, Texas Tech University; Dusty L. Palmer, Texas Tech University*

Leadership Development from an Intercultural Lens: Three Examples of Education Efforts that Cross Global Borders. *Arnold B. Danzig, San Jose State University/Arizona State University Emeritus; Zorka Karanxha, University of South Florida; Parinaz Zartoshty, San Jose State University; Ulviyya Tofiq Mikayilova, ADA University; Eduardo Rafael Munoz-Munoz, San José State University*

Navigating Context through Situated Professional Learning: Reflections from Novice Middle Leaders in Hong Kong. *Chun Sing Maxwell Ho, The Education University of Hong Kong; Darren A. Bryant, Curtin University; Allan David Walker, The Education University of Hong Kong*

Chair: *Carla Finkelstein, Towson University*

79.072-5. Unsettling Empire through Indigenous Histories (Table 5). Division F - Historical Inquiry in Education; Roundtable Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Collective Memory of the Nigerian Civil War through Literary Narratives. *Damilare Tella, West Virginia University*
Defining Restorative: Educator discourses, white supremacy, and resistance. *Ceema Samimi, University of Minnesota; Nox Zand-Dow, University of Minnesota*

He Awa Whiria: Reimagining Education Research through the Braiding of Mātauranga Māori and Future-Facing Inquiry. *Te Hurinui RENATA Karaka-Clarke, University of Waikato*
The Sounds of Mexican Secularism. Religion, Music Education, and the Creation of Peasant Culture in Mexico's Post-revolutionary School Reform. *Marino Miranda Noriega, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Unforgetting the UN's Language Histories: Tracing Linguistic Culture and Policy Shifts from 1945 to 2025. *Honorine Ntoh Yuh, University of Alabama*

Chair: *Lauri Johnson, Boston College*

79.072-6. Being, Belonging, and Becoming in School and Community (Table 6). Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Being and Becoming in Many Worlds: A Sudanese Scholar's Journey Through Power, Place, and Educational Reform. *Jubara AbuSin, Pennsylvania State University*

Exceptional Spaces: Diverse Learning Environments in a Public High School. *Karlyn J Gorski, University of Chicago*

"I Feel Like I Won't Be Smart Enough." The Bidirectional Relationship between Belonging and Academics. *Sebastian Castrechini, Stanford University; Kristin Geiser, John W. Gardner Center for Youth and Their Communities, Stanford University*

Lifting as We Rise: Profesora Testimonios de school, comunidad, familia. *Joanna Maravilla, Lewis University; Juana Maria Reyes, Lewis University; Elvira Pichardo, Lewis University; Erica R. Davila, Lewis University*

79.072-7. Cultivating Global Citizens: Agency and Belonging in World Education (Table 7). Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Becoming A Global Citizen: A Daily Perspective of the Language Education in Urban Families in East China. *Yajing Hang, Zhejiang Shuren University; Rui Zhao, Zhejiang Shuren University*

Children's Agency, Cultural Identities, and Learning in a Chinese Immersion Preschool: Insights from the Little Tiger Community. *Li Tan, University of Texas Austin*

Striving Upward Across the Urban-Rural Divide: Intergenerational Occupational Aspiration of Migrant and Urban Native Adolescents in China. *Qiyin Fan, East China Normal University; Jiamin Cheng, East China Normal University; Haolun Xie, Beijing Normal University*

Understanding Belonging and Academic Struggles Among Micronesian Students in Oregon. *Kaeleen Anne Kirkpatrick, University of Portland*

Chair: *Qiyin Fan, East China Normal University*

79.072-8. Motivation, Care, and Resilience: Sustaining a Transformative Educational Journey (Table 8). Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

How Social Support Influence L2 Chinese Learning Motivation Among Hong Kong Ethnic Minority Students. *Ziqi Zhang, Hong Kong Polytechnic University; Xinhua Zhu, Hong Kong Polytechnic University; Zhengli Xie, The Education University of Hong Kong; Wanru Pang, The Hong Kong Polytechnic University*

Moving beyond Whited Prestige Perceptions in Korean English Education for Psychosocial Sustainability and Enhanced Learning. *Pauli Badenhorst, University of Texas - Rio Grande Valley; MinSoo Kim-Bossard, The College of*

New Jersey; Younkyung Hong, Ball State University
Navigating Care and Autonomy: Understanding the Post-Graduation Mobility Decisions of Chinese Female International Graduates. *Fengyi Lin, Peking University; Jialu Wang, Peking University; Wenqin Shen, Peking University*
Transformative Journey to Critical Scholarship: Counterstories of East Asian Doctoral Students Through the Lens of AsianCrit. *Xiaolu Zhang, George Mason University; Jihyae Choe, George Mason University; Yueyang Shen, Boston College*

Chair: *Pauli Badenhorst, University of Texas - Rio Grande Valley*

79.072-9. Reimagining Educational Research for and with Latine Students (Table 9). Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Sentémos y Hablemos: The Impact of Home Visits for Chronically Absent Students in Spanish Homes. *Andrea Amado Giampetruzzi, Yale University; Jacob Sale Werblow, Central Connecticut State University*

The Power of our Mestiza Praxis: Undergraduate Chicanas Building Critical Literacy in Community to Enact Change. *Elena Marie Marquez, Chapman University*

Networks of Care: Educator Perspectives on Supporting Central American Unaccompanied Minors in U.S. Schools. *Stephany Cuevas, Chapman University; Martha C. Franco, California State University - Long Beach*

Strengthening Ties: The Role of Parent Engagement in School Satisfaction among Latinx Parents of English Learners. *Nicole Pina, University of California - Los Angeles*

Chair: *Beatriz E. Quintos, University of Maryland*

79.072-10. Researching with African Diasporas in the Latinidad (Table 10). Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Nou' la! Ubuntu and In Lak'ech: Repositioning Black Scholars in the Latine Diaspora. *Stephanie Renee Anckle, City of Long Beach; Lorri J. Santamaría, California Lutheran University*

Black Joy as Praxis: Institutional Transformation at California Hispanic-Serving Institutions. *Tramaine Austin-Dillon, San Francisco State University*

Evaluation of the African Caribbean Black Family Group Conferencing (ACB-FGC) Project: Pilot Data. *Lance Trevor McCready, University of Toronto - OISE*

Chair: *Cleveland Hayes, Indiana University - Indianapolis*

79.073. AERA Roundtable Session Saturday 3:45 pm - Gold 1; Roundtable Session

79.073-1. Roundtable Session 8: Student Learning and Development in College and Beyond (Table 1). Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Exploring Academic Self-Efficacy and Related Factors Among First-Year Agriculture College Students. *Ashley Thompson, The Ohio State University; Kellie Claflin, The Ohio State University; Faith Galavich, The Ohio State University*

Promoting Career Self-Efficacy among Low-Income College Students: A Mixed Methods Examination. *Joseph Kitchen, University of Southern California; Shinji Katsumoto, University of Southern Mississippi; Ronald Hallett, University of Southern California*

Supporting Retention and Career Development in Computer Science: A Multi-Level Needs Assessment of Low-Income First-Year Students. *Nicholas Burkhart, University of Cincinnati; Justin Zhan, University of Cincinnati; Youn Seon Lim, University of Cincinnati; Whitney Gaskins, University of Cincinnati; Daniel Dong, University of Cincinnati; Michelle Encalada, University of Cincinnati; Julia A. Holton, University of Cincinnati*

The Benefits of Learning Assistant Programs for Professional Skill Acquisition. *Amanda N. Nix, Florida State University; Joseph O'Shea, Florida State University; Shouping Hu, Florida State University*

79.073-2. Dual Enrollment & Higher Education (Table 2).

Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Dual Enrollment and the Purpose of Higher Education: Mapping Our Assumptions Toward a Broader Research Agenda. *Julia C. Duncheon, University of Washington; Reid T. Sagara, University of Washington; David S. Knight, University of Washington*

Imagined Futures: Inspiring the Next Generation of Educators through Dual Enrollment Programming. *Jennifer Michelle Johnson, Temple University; Jawaria Ashraf, Temple University*

Dual-Credit Dosage: Conceptual, Methodological, and Empirical Patterns. *Matthew S. Giani, University of Texas at Austin; Rashi Agarwal, University of Texas at Austin; Madison E. Andrews, University of Texas at Austin; Kait Ogden, University of Texas at Austin*

79.073-3. Prominent Considerations in Faculty and Research Collaborations (Table 3). Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Factors Shaping Faculty Collaboration: A Case Study from a Resource-Constrained Setting. *Samuel Getnet Abate, The Education University of Hong Kong*

Navigating Undergraduate Research, Scholarship, and Creative Inquiry: Faculty Experiences in U.S. Research Universities. *Gokce Garip, Gazi University; Gurcu Koc, Gazi University*

To Collaborate or Not: Researchers' Intention for International Research Collaboration: The Theory of Planned Behavior. *Anil Ersöz, Middle East Technical University; Pelin Yuce, Middle East Technical University; Sevgi Kaya Kaşıkçı, Middle East Technical University; Yasar Kondakci, Middle East Technical University; Merve Zayim-Kurtay, Middle East Technical University*

Chair: *Gokce Garip, Gazi University*

79.073-4. Challenging Neutrality: Educators Shaping Social Justice and Reflective Practice in Education (Table 4). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Exploring Ethnically Diverse Students' Awareness of Famous Scientists and Links To Critical Reflection. *Chelsea McElwee, University of California - Riverside; LeNisha R. Williams, University of California - Riverside; Aerika Brittian Loyd, University of California - Riverside*

Refusing to Romanticize: Preservice Teachers Confront and Avoid the Inadequacies of Plantation Field Trips. *Meghan Moore-Hubbard, Kennesaw State University*

The Misuse of Developmental Frameworks in Historical Thinking. *Anna Falkner, University of Memphis; Noreen Naseem Rodriguez, Michigan State University*

We Were Never Meant to Be Neutral: Black Millennial and Gen-Z Teachers Shaping Social Studies. *Jazmin Claxton, University of Texas at Austin*

Chair: *Jazmin Claxton, University of Texas at Austin*

79.073-5. Healing and Honoring: Black Teachers' Practices Across Time (Table 5). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Centering the Legacy of Black Educators in Teacher Education. *Natasha A. Thornton, Spelman College*

Disrupting Deficit Thinking: Black Teachers Reclaim Culturally Responsive Practice. *Mia Rollack, Eastern Michigan University*

Exploring Two Teachers' Culturally Responsive and Sustaining Considerations in Response to Intervention Implementation. *Joyce M. Gomez-Najarro, California State University - Fullerton*

The Raciolinguistic Embodiment of a Black Teacher Hearing Black Language Speakers in an Elementary Classroom.

Alice Y. Lee, University of California - Riverside

Through the Eyes of Liberation: Black Teacher Candidates Reclaiming Literacy Through Culturally Sustainable Practice. *Heather C Blackwell, Morgan State University*

79.073-6. The Teachers Are Not OK: Supporting Teacher Well-Being, Motivation, & Engagement (Table 6).

Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Effective Online Communities of Practice for K-12 Teachers: A Meta-Aggregation of Qualitative Studies. *Idam Kim, Florida State University; Secil Caskurlu, Florida State University; Sihan Jian, Florida State University; Hilal Ayan, Florida State University*

Exploring the Causal Structure Among Perceived Student Behavior Challenges, Teacher Stress, Emotion Regulation, and Self-Efficacy Using Algorithm-Based Discovery Methods. *Fang Wang, University of South Carolina; Ruiqin Gao, University of South Carolina; Dexin Shi, University of South Carolina*

“I Can’t Even Look at Her!”: Negotiation of Emotional Labor in Teachers’ Discourse about Parents. *Idit Fast, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev; Dana Vedder-Weiss, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev*

Procedural Justice, Public Service Motivation, and Teacher Well-Being Influencing Work Engagement in Indian Schools. *Deepak Sharma, Indian Institute of Management; Furkan Khan, Indian Institute of Management*

Teachers’ work engagement during and after the COVID-19 pandemic: A five-year longitudinal study. *Kenji Tsuyuguchi, Ehime University; Tetsuo Kuramoto, Shizuoka University Art and Culture*

Chair: *Monica B. Glina, New York Medical College*

79.073-7. Beyond the Tools: Equity, Tech, and Global Teacher Learning (Table 7).

Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Exploring High School Teachers’ GenAI use through the Culturally Responsive Teaching Lens. *Rukmini Manasa Avadhanam, University of Illinois at Chicago; Jolie V. Kennedy, Empire State University - SUNY*

Measuring School-Based Social Support for Inclusive Education (SSS-IE) in South Korea. *Joonheon Kwon, Korea University; IN SUK RYU, Korea University; Dakyeom Lee, Korea University; Haerin Park, University of Saint Joseph; Seunghyun Son, Korea University; So Yoon Kim, Korea*

University

Navigating Diversity, Equity and Inclusion (DEI), and Culturally Sustaining Pedagogy in Teacher Education. *Samira Said Al Hosni, Indiana University*

Navigating Technology Integration in Vietnamese Lower Secondary Schools During Curriculum Reform. *Vu Phuc Phuong Dao, University of Minnesota*

Does AI-TPACK Affect Teacher’s Professional Confidence? A Survey Study of K-12 and Pre-service Teachers. *Jiahui Qi, East China Normal University; Dandan Gao, East China Normal University*

Chair: *Rukmini Manasa Avadhanam, University of Illinois at Chicago*

79.074. AERA Roundtable Session Saturday 3:45 pm - Gold 2;
Roundtable Session

79.074-1. Enacting and Improving School Choice Systems (Table 1).

Division L - Educational Policies and Politics;

Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;

3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Mapping neoliberal education reform: A spatial analysis of charter schools in New Jersey. *David Osworth, University of North Carolina - Greensboro; M. Nathan Tanner, University of Nevada - Reno; Emily Kennedy, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Open Enrollment Policies, School Segregation, and Redefining the Role of the State in Public Education. *Eli Rolfes, Vanderbilt University; Maury Nation, Vanderbilt University*

Designing Effective Public-Private Partnerships in Education. *Harry Patrinos, University of Arkansas*

Chair: *Paul S. Myers, Indiana University*

79.074-2. Contested Classrooms: Censorship, Polarization, and Teacher Policy in U.S. Education (Table 2).

Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Political and Psychological Predictors of Parents’ School Censorship in the United States. *Sarah Farnsworth Hatch, Harvard University; Hannah Castner, Harvard University*

The Adoption of Alternate Route Teacher Certification Laws Among US States. *Jennifer Lauren Nelson, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Anand Swaminathan, Emory University; Demetrius Lewis, University of California - Riverside*

The Narratives and Discourses of Texas Teachers: Stories, Beliefs, Attitudes, and Perceptions in an Era of Heightened Book Challenges and Book Censorship. *Erin Ashcraft, University of North Texas*

Who Do You Talk to? —Discussant Network Analysis among

Missouri Civics Teachers amid Polarization. *Chaebong Nam, University of Missouri - St. Louis; Suhwon Lee, University of Missouri*

Chair: *Deborah Loewenberg Ball, University of Michigan*
Discussant: *Patience Amadu, University of Colorado - Colorado Springs*

79.074-3. Double Reduction, Multiple Realities: Policy Implementation, Adaptation, and Impact in China's Education System (Table 3). Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Feedback Loops and Policy Evolution: China's Burden Reduction Revisited through Tools and Narratives. *Jia Li, East China Normal University; Zhenfei Peng, East China Normal University*

How School Leaders Navigate Holistic Development Amid China's Double Reduction Policy. *Yanyan Miao, James Cook University - Singapore; M Akshir Ab Kadir, James Cook University - Singapore; Jagdeep Kaur, James Cook University - Singapore*

How the Implementation Deviation of the "Double Reduction" Policy Happens: A Case Study in Chengdu. *XUEYANG MO, Beijing Normal University*

The causal effect of China's "Double Reduction" Policy on Primary School Students' Creativity and Academic Achievement. *Jinyan Zhou, Beijing Normal University*

Understanding Student Enrollment in Advanced Courses: The Implementation of Washington's Academic Acceleration Policy. *Megan Austin, American Institutes for Research; Preeya Pandya Mbekeani, American Institutes for Research*

Chair: *Cheng Chang, Binghamton University - SUNY*

79.074-4. Expanding the Boundaries of Lesson Study: Innovation, Equity, and Community in STEM Education (Table 4). SIG-Lesson Study; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Preservice Teachers' Lesson Study Insights: Using ChatGPT to Help Multilingual Learners Comprehend Mathematical Story Problems. *Sheida Moghtader Eslami, University of Florida; Kayla Sutcliffe, University of Florida; Melissa M. Soto, University of Florida; Kristen Apraiz, University of Florida; Aimaral Tabarak, University of Florida; Ri Ayat Ainul Bashirah, University of Florida; Hongze Zhu, University of Florida; Hong Zhang, University of Florida*

AI is a New Partner: Enhancing Teaching through AI-Powered Lesson Study. *chenlu liu, East China Normal University; Zheng Xin, East China Normal University*

Fostering Data Literacy Through Community-Driven STEM Projects: A Lesson Study Investigation. *Rongjin Huang,*

Middle Tennessee State University; Dovie Kimmins, Middle Tennessee State University; Jeremy Winters, Middle Tennessee State University; Fonya Scott, Middle Tennessee State University; Mark Ikhifa, Middle Tennessee State University

Chair: *Andrew A. Hunte, University of the West Indies - Five Islands*

Discussant: *Johana E. Thomas Zapata, Washington State University*

79.074-5. Policy Contexts for Music Education (Table 5). SIG-Music Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

A Systems-focused Analysis of Equity in Access to Music Education in Kentucky. *David S. Miller, University of Kentucky*

Music Educators' Perceptions of Policy Language from Divisive Concepts Laws. *Karen Salvador, Michigan State University; Ryan D. Shaw, Michigan State University*

The Voice of Policy: A National Content Analysis of "Gendered" U.S. All-State Choir Policies. *Joshua Palkki, Georgia Institute of Technology; Dillon Beede, Columbia University; Tatyana Louis-Jacques, University of North Texas; Katie Smith, University of Michigan*

Elementary General Music Realities: Comparing NAFME's Opportunity to Learn Standards with Current Schedules and Resources. *Erika J. Knapp, Texas Woman's University; Karen Salvador, Michigan State University*

Chair: *Bri'Ann Wright, California State University - Fullerton*

79.074-6. Centering Mentor Teachers, Transforming Residencies: Equity-Driven Mentoring and Professional Learning in SUPs (Table 6). SIG-School-University Partnership Research; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Centering Mentor Teachers in Clinically-Based Teacher Education: A Research Synthesis of U.S. Mentoring Practices. *Seth A. Parsons, George Mason University; Kristien Zenkov, George Mason University; Audra Parker, George Mason University; Valeisha Ellis, Spelman College; Danielle V. Dennis, University of Rhode Island*

Constructing a New Vision for Teacher Residents' Development: The Complexities of Implementing Professional Learning within School-University Partnerships. *Valerie Hill-Jackson, Texas A&M University*

How do Higher Education Institutions Need to Adapt to Sustain Equity-Driven Teacher Residency Programs? *Catherine A. Lammert, Texas Tech University; Fanni Liu Coward, Texas Tech University*

Discussant: *David C. Virtue, Western Carolina University*

79.074-7. Innovative Quantitative Analyses: Examining Language and Literacy Development around the Globe (Table 7). SIG-Second Language Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

- Constructing Cross-Cultural Meanings Across Nested Timescales Through Digital Video Composing in an EFL Context. *Qianqian Ma, University at Buffalo - SUNY*
- Latent Profiles of EFL Reading Strategies: Socio-Demographics and Implications for Instruction. *Yuyan Xia, University of Kentucky; Na Liu, Zhejiang Ocean University; Lei Zhao, Chongqing University of Education*
- Morphological Analysis in Explaining Morphological Awareness with Its Association to Language and Reading Skills. *Joong won Lee, Hankuk University of Foreign Studies; Young-Suk Grace Kim, University of California - Irvine*
- The 'How Long' Question: English Language Learning Trajectories in Australian Schools. *Lucy Lu, Australian Education Research Organisation; Olivia Groves, Australian Education Research Organisation; Wai-Yin Wan, NSW Department of Education and Communities; Jennifer Hammond, University of Technology - Sydney*

Chair: *Tuba Yilmaz, University of Utah*

79.074-8. Learning and Belonging in Out-of-School Contexts: Multilingual Learners' Agency and Community Engagement (Table 8). SIG-Second Language Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

- Expanding Academic Learning Opportunities for Newcomer Multilingual Students in Secondary School. *Adam R. Moylan, Rockman et al; Alex M. Gurn, Rockman et al Cooperative*
- Learning English in the Real World: Investigating Live-Abroad Accompanying Wives' Learner Agency. *Angelica Ribeiro, University of Houston - Clear Lake; Shuyi Yang, Johns Hopkins University*
- Narratives of Belonging: Evaluating the Extended Family Model in Community-centered Programming for Immigrant Communities. *Lan Quach Kolano, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Jue Wang, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Emilia Olivera, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Michele Falla, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Kristen Rebecca Cruz, University of North Carolina - Charlotte*

Chair: *Kellie Rolstad, University of Maryland*

79.074-9. Storywork, Healing, and Creative Sovereignities:

Indigenous Pedagogies of Resurgence Across Lands, Languages, and Generations (Table 9). SIG-Indigenous Peoples of the Americas; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

- Como Los Antiguos Caminantes: Walking the Land Undoing Learning with Indigenous Grassroots Research. *Ymasumac Marañón Davis, University of San Diego*
- Indigenous Normal Schools: the struggle to build an intellectual formation? *Raul Olmo Fregoso Bailón, University of Nevada - Reno*
- Queering Reindigenization: Grief, Language Nests, and Diasporic Healing in the Salvadoran Diaspora. *Claudia Alvarenga, University of California - Los Angeles*
- Teachings from a Diné youth: Representing Hozho through story. *Tifiny Mills, Utah State University; Christina Morgan, Utah State University; Eileen Quintana, Nebo School District; Breanne K. Litts, Utah State University; Dallas Haws, Utah State University; Analyssa Allison, Nebo Title VI Indian Education; Natalie Billie, Nebo Title VI Indian Education Program*
- Discussant: *Miguel Angel Garcia-Bocanegra, Northwestern University*

79.075. AERA Roundtable Session Saturday 3:45 pm - Gold 3; Roundtable Session

79.075-1. Designing Pedagogy and Practice in the Age of AI (Table 1). SIG-Technology as an Agent of Change in Teaching and Learning; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

- From Planning to Practice: Insights from Teacher Technology Leaders' Experiences Designing Generative AI Professional Learning. *Kristin Børte, University of Bergen; Jessa Henderson, University of Bergen*
- Co-constructing Computational Thinking in Early Childhood Education: Investigating Dynamics of Co-design between Researchers and Teachers by Epistemic Network Analysis. *Xuechun SHI, University of Hong Kong; Shuang Wu, East China Normal University; Zhichun Liu, University of Hong Kong; Shen Ba, The Education University of Hong Kong*
- Designing a Teacher Learning Trajectory to Support AI and NLP Integration in Middle School Science. *Daria Smyslova, North Carolina State University; Srijita Chakraburty, Indiana University; Oluwatomisin Obajemu, University of Florida; Krista D. Glazewski, North Carolina State University; Cindy E. Hmelo-Silver, Indiana University; Kristy E. Boyer, University of Florida*
- Developing Design Principles to Strategically Integrate ChatGPT into EFL Writing through an Activity Theory Perspective. *YUNAN ZHANG, University of Hong Kong;*

Yongcan Liu, University of Cambridge

Chair: *Lauren Bagdy, University of Georgia*

79.075-2. Navigating the Landscape of Digital Divide in Education (Table 2). SIG-Technology as an Agent of Change in Teaching and Learning; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

The Digital Divide of Technology Resources: A Longitudinal Examination of Technology Resource Data from K12 Schools. *Matthew L. Wilson, Kennesaw State University; Laurie Brantley-Dias, Kennesaw State University; Austin Brown, Kennesaw State University; Naima Fouad-Gilliam, Kennesaw State University*

Bridging the Digital Divide: Analyzing Teacher Technology Acceptance and Use in Underserved Regions. *Wen Li, Beijing Normal University; Rui Jiang, Beijing Normal University; Qian Zhao, Beijing Normal University*

Beyond the Digital Divide: Sociodemographic Gradients in College Students' Generative AI Usage, Literacy, and Attitudes. *Ran Liu, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Carla Z. Glave, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

MOOC Chatbot Adoption and Learning Outcomes: Students' Socioeconomic Regions and Navigational Behaviors. *Songhee Han, Florida State University; Min Liu, University of Texas at Austin*

Chair: *Matthew L. Wilson, Kennesaw State University*

79.075-3. Dual Language Programmatic Planning and Design (Table 3). SIG-Bilingual Education Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

"We'd Never Been Asked Before": Critical Listening and Collaborative Curriculum Co-Design in Dual-Language Education. *Grace Cornell Gonzales, University of Washington*

Adapting to Changes in California's English Learner Population. *Laura Hill, Public Policy Institute of California; Beyond Jonathan Deng, Public Policy Institute of California*

Emergent Bilinguals in a Chinese-English DLBE Program: Navigating Opportunities, Challenges, and Positionings. *Peizhu Liu, University of Pennsylvania*

English Learners in Dual Language Programs: Evidence from Middle School Through College Enrollment. *Trey Miller, University of Texas - Dallas; Camila Morales, University of Texas - Dallas; Lynn Morgan, University of Texas - Dallas; Gema Zamarro, University of Arkansas*

From Placemaking to Placekeeping: Learning from Equity-Based Urban Planning to Address Gentrification in Dual-Language Programs. *Steve Daniel Przymus, University of Rhode Island*

79.075-4. Identities, Communities and Voices in DLBE (Table 4). SIG-Bilingual Education Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

From Sociocultural Competence to Transculturing as a Goal of Dual Language Bilingual Education. *Juan A. Freire, Brigham Young University; Jongyeon Joy Ee, Loyola Marymount University; Zhongfeng Tian, Rutgers University - Newark*

Improving Dual Language Immersion School Climate: Perspectives of Administrators and Teachers. *Nicholas C. Block, Biola University; Marlen Quintero Pérez, California State University - Northridge*

Interrogating constructs of linguistic equity: Latine families in Mandarin-English dual language immersion. *Catherine Park, University of California - Berkeley*

Monoglossic and transglossic tensions in a Mandarin dual language bilingual education classroom: An ethnographic-case study of circulating language ideologies and their impact. *Vashti Wai Yu Lee, Brigham Young University*

Naming and Erasure: Rethinking the 'English Speaker' Label in Dual Language Bilingual Education. *Jongyeon Joy Ee, Loyola Marymount University*

79.075-5. Languages and languaging within technical and adaptive contexts: STEM revisited (Table 5). SIG-Bilingual Education Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Research-Practice Partnerships in Dual Language Settings: Spanish Oral Language Progressions in Mathematics for Multilingual Learners. *Elvira G. Armas, Loyola Marymount University; Magaly Lavadenz, Loyola Marymount University; Kaivan Yuen, Montebello Unified School District; Linda R. G. Kaminski, Loyola Marymount University*

Translanguaging Pedagogy in U.S. K-12 STEM Classrooms: A Systematic Meta-Synthesis Abstract. *Sujin Kim, George Mason University; Manqian Zhao, George Mason University; Woomee Kim, George Mason University; Bilgehan Ayik, George Mason University; Dai Gu, George Mason University; Xiaowen Chen, George Mason University; Yixin Zan, George Mason University; Kathleen Ramos, George Mason University*

Empirical Profiling of High School Bilingual Students' Perceptions of STEM Learning Environment. *Hector H. Rivera, Texas A&M University; Heesun Chang, Texas A&M University; Amin Raeisi-Vanani, Texas A&M University; Yiming Zhu, Texas A&M University; Eun Hye Grace Ko, Texas A&M University*

79.075-6. Towards a Justice-Oriented Bilingual Education (Table 6). SIG-Bilingual Education Research; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

“Not Just Portuguese”: Translanguaging and Linguistic Justice for Indigenous and Refugee Students in Brazilian Schools. *Michelle Angelo-Rocha, University of South Florida; Karina O. De Paula, Texas Tech University; Cátia Regina Guidio Alves de Oliveira, Brazilian National Council for Scientific and Technological Development; Kevin Donley, Georgetown University; Lauren Braunstein, University of South Florida*

25 Years of Research on Classified English Learners in U.S. Schools: A Scoping Review. *Brenda Valdes, Stanford University; Amado M. Padilla, Stanford University; Oswaldo Rosales, Stanford University*

A Foucauldian genealogy of spatial and material discourses in U.S. bilingual education. *Seon Ja Chang, University of Georgia*

Constructing a New Vision of Assessments: Centering Emergent Bilinguals’ Linguistic Repertoires for Equity and Justice. *Angeles Munoz, University of North Texas / Texas Woman’s University*

Critical Constructions: A Snapshot of a Black Student’s Biliteracy Practices in a DLBE Program. *Brittany Frieson, University of Texas at Austin; Vania Ledesma, University of Texas at Austin*

79.075-7. The Architecture of Accessibility in the Academy: Structures, Experiences, and the Spaces Between (Table 7). SIG-Disability Studies in Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Passing for What? Disability, Delay, and the Architecture of Academic Recognition. *Alan R. Foley, Syracuse University*

Serendipitous Landscapes: A Narrative History of Disability Accessibility at Arizona State University. *Jennifer R. Miller, Arizona State University*

“Where the Path Goes through a Tree”: Failure of Ensure Spatial Accessibility and Instructional Inclusivity in Higher Education in India. *Arpita Sarker, University of Iowa*

Chair: *Sarah Dubin, Rowan University*

79.075-8. Perspectives and Practices of AI Use Across Educational and Global Contexts (Table 8). SIG-

Language and Social Processes; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Learning to Use GenAI for Scholarly Publication: Challenges from a Global South Perspective. *Peter I. De Costa, Michigan State University; Nari Kim, Michigan State*

University; Joanne Cheng, Michigan State University; Hendriwanto Hendriwanto, Michigan State University

Examining Trust in AI: Analyzing Teacher Candidates’ Discourse in Response to Automated Feedback. *Kayla Michelle Reist, University of Virginia; Peter A. Youngs, University of Virginia*

Language Ideology Exploration as a Pathway to Critical AI Integration in Teacher Preparation. *Danette Y. Martinez, University of Texas - San Antonio; Kathryn I. Henderson, University of Texas - San Antonio; Jennifer Gilardi Swoyer, University of Texas - San Antonio; Bedrettin Yazan, University of Texas - San Antonio; Gabriella Martinez, University of Texas - San Antonio*

Chair: *Peter I. De Costa, Michigan State University*

79.076. AERA Roundtable Session Saturday 3:45 pm - Gold 4; Roundtable Session

79.076-1. Translanguaging, Text, and the Aesthetics of Learning: Expanding the Boundaries of Disciplinary Literacies (Table 1). SIG-Language and Social Processes; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

A Comparison of Math Word Problem Text Features in the U.S. and China. *Rulan Wu, Texas A&M University; Michelle Nguyen Kwok, Texas A&M University*

Development and Validation of a Questionnaire to Document Elementary School Students’ Translanguaging and Transmodalizing Attitudes and Use in Science Learning. *Kexin Zhang, University of Georgia; Ai-Chu Elisha Ding, University of Georgia; Katherine Martin, University of Georgia; Jorge Hernandez Cervantes, Placeholder*

Toward a Theory of Shenanigans in Disciplinary Literacies: Aesthetics of Humor in Social Life. *Scott Storm, University at Albany - SUNY; Karis Michelle Jones, Baylor University*

Chair: *Scott Storm, University at Albany - SUNY*

79.076-2. Education at cross-roads: Education and Cultural Perspectives Across Nations (Table 2). SIG-International Studies; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

All Children Succeeding: Understanding the Inclusive Education Landscape in Uzbekistan. *Christine Elaine Ashby, Syracuse University; Beth Myers, Syracuse University; Julia M. White, Syracuse University; Kate Lapham; Sara H. Petit-McClure, Syracuse University; Shana Lewis, Syracuse University; Deborah Taub, OTL Education Solutions*

Dialogic teaching as a democratic response in a post-truth era: a cross-cultural theoretical analysis. *Shuying Li, University of Nottingham*

Towards a model of culturally sustaining pedagogy for Roma youth. *Raquel Sáenz Ortiz, Southwestern University; Hannah I. Caceres, Southwestern University; Ximena Ling Uribe, Southwestern University; Alba Salazar Jiménez, Universidad de Sevilla*

Chair: *Abdurasheed Olatunji Abdussalam, Visiting Prof at McGill University*

79.076-3. Critical Examination of Race, Ethnicity, Class, and Gender Roundtable: Strategic Battles, From Surviving to Thriving in Educational Contexts (Table 3). SIG-Critical Examination of Race, Ethnicity, Class and Gender in Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Side-Stepping the Colonial Matrix: How Black and Latinx Leaders Imagine and Build Equity. *Maria Del Carmen Unda, University of Texas at Austin; Angela Valenzuela, University of Texas at Austin; Kait Ogden, University of Texas at Austin; Jacob Navarrete, University of Texas at Austin*

Moving from Suffering to Survive to Thriving: Exploring the Impact of Systemic Racism and White Supremacy on Black PWI Staff. *Jennifer Taylor Edens, California State University - East Bay; Robert Lindsey, Johnson C. Smith University*

Community Cultural Wealth of Global South Immigrant Math Teachers in U.S. Classrooms. *Seda Ozbek-Damar, Arizona State University; Saesaem Yoon, University of Washington - Tacoma; Tipsuda Chaomuangkhong, Arizona State University*

Chair: *Jawanza Kalonji Rand, Teachers College, Columbia University*

79.076-4. Spaces of Sound, Memory, and Meaning in Hip Hop Education (Table 4). SIG-Hip Hop Theories, Praxis & Pedagogies; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Culturally Inappropriate: Cliche and the Power of Owning Your Story, Masters, and Hustle in Hip-Hop. *Stephen Walker, University of Pittsburgh; Marlene N. Fares, Kutztown University of Pennsylvania*

Experiences of Undergraduate Volunteers in a Hip-Hop Music Program for Incarcerated Youth. *David DeAngelis, Syracuse University; Patrick Horton, Ball State University*

Unforgetting and Imagining: Student-Created Albums as Investigation of In-Service Music Educator Identity Augmentation - An Ode to [Anonymous Addressee]. *Drew Xavier Coles, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Voice, Vibe, and Place: Rewriting Spatial Histories Through Hip Hop Aesthetics. *Viraj V. Patel, Illinois State University;*

Rabani Garg, University of Pennsylvania

Chair: *Larry C. Bryant, Metro State University*

79.076-5. Literacies of Equity and Liberation in Higher Education (Table 5). SIG-Writing and Literacies;

Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Language Literacies of Intersectionality: Women Academics' Critical Dialogues on Race, Gender, and Place. *Dianne T. Wellington, SUNY - College at Cortland; Amy Walker, Kent State University; Kerry H. Alexander, University of Maryland; Jasmyn K. Jones, University of Memphis*
Reimagining FYC: Justice-Driven Visions for Learning and Liberation. *Anna Carolina Peñaloza, University of California - Davis; Sanjana Dhamankar, University of California - Davis; Ana Delmy Castellon, University of California - Davis*

The Hegemony of the 'Lone(ly) Scholar' Archetype: PhD Students' Writing Support Networks, Equity, and Belonging. *Kira J. Baker-Doyle, University of Illinois at Chicago; Kristine Wilber, University of Illinois at Chicago*

Chair: *Maggie Mnayer, Central Michigan University*

79.076-6. RT2: Quantitative Advances and Approaches to Research on Inclusion, Equity, Educational Disparities and Student Success (Table 6). Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Effects of Selected Language-Related Factors on Reading Performance: A Finite Mixture Growth Modeling Study. *Robyn Mennella, Long Island University - Brookville*

Predicting Inclusion: Institutional Correlates of Transgender-Inclusive Policies in U.S. Public Universities using Machine Learning Analysis. *Amanda J. Davis Simpfenderfer, College of William & Mary; Ailidh Wallace, College of William & Mary; Travis Heath Olson, Michigan State University; Obed Amoakoh Boateng, Virginia Commonwealth University; Kamden Strunk, Virginia Commonwealth University; Jason C. Garvey, University of Vermont; Mario I Suárez, Utah State University*

Geospatial Analysis of Higher Education Students' Critical-Thinking Skills. *Doris Zahner, Council for Aid to Education; Jouni Vettenranta, University of Jyväskylä; Heidi M. Hyytinen, University of Helsinki; Jani Ursin, University of Jyväskylä*

Longitudinal Latent Models and the Potential for Equity in a Post-Race Consciousness Policy Environment. *Tafadzwa Tivaringe, Spencer Foundation*

79.076-7. Learning Where we Live: Reimagining STEM

Through Community Practices (Table 7). Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

Designing for the Future: Latine Mothers' Imagined Technologies for Family Learning. *Julie Salazar, University of California - Irvine; June Ahn, University of California - Irvine; Andres Sebastian Bustamante, University of California - Irvine*

Family Math in Practice: Early Math Knowledge Making with Black and Latina Mothers. *Susana Beltran-Grimm, Portland State University; Karlena Diane Ochoa, California State University - Fullerton; Yemimah King, Georgia State University; Sasha Reinwald Albrecht, Portland State University*

Family Learning Across Daily Routines and Implications for STEM Educational Activity Design. *Daniela Alvarez-Vargas, Colorado State University*

Culturally Responsive Play: Co-Design of Early Math Games with Latine Families. *Vanessa Bermudez, Loyola Marymount University; Britney Meza-Camacho, University of California - Irvine; Haidi M. Peñaloza Torres, University of California - Irvine; Andres Sebastian Bustamante, University of California - Irvine*

Chairs: *Julie Salazar, University of California - Irvine; Daniela Alvarez-Vargas, Colorado State University*

Discussant: *Karlena Diane Ochoa, California State University - Fullerton*

79.076-8. Comics, Literature, Animation, and the Arts as Curricular Frames (Table 8). Division B - Curriculum Studies; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

From Appropriation to Allyship: Representation of Cultural Values in Disney/Pixar's Animated Animals. *Jacki Fitzpatrick, Texas Tech University; Rajib Ahmed Faisal, Texas Tech University*

Interrogating the Literacies of Black Boys and Building Curricular Connections in Comics, Literature, and Pop Culture. *Christian M. Hines, Texas State University; Erik Hines, George Mason University*

Rooted and Rising: Empowering Futures Through Identity and Expression in African American Studies, Financial Literacies, and the Arts. *Diana Isern, New York City Department of Education; Qiana Spellman, St. John's University; Shannah M. Henderson Amare, New York City Department of Education*

Chair: *Kristen Schaffer, Mount Royal University*

Division and SIG Posters

79.077. AERA Poster Session Saturday 3:45 pm; Poster Session

79.077-1. Division D Graduate Student In-Progress Research Poster Session. Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Invited Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 3:45-5:15pm

Posters:

1. A Meta-Analysis of the Effects of LLM-Generated Feedback on Assessed Writing Outcomes in L2 Contexts (Poster 1). *Huanxiao Wang, University of Pennsylvania; Yucheng Cao, Middle Tennessee State University*
2. A Mixed Method Study on MOOC Learners' Behavioral Intention to Use an Educational Chatbot (Poster 2). *Jueun Shin, Florida State University; Songhee Han, Florida State University*
3. A Simulation-Based Comparison Between Estimated Latent Scores and Sum Scores (Poster 3). *Tonatiuh Xochihua Tlecuil, University of California - Los Angeles; Craig K. Enders, University of California - Los Angeles; Yi Feng, University of California - Los Angeles*
4. Accept or Resist Physics Laboratory: A Comparative Study Between Urban and Rural Middle School Teachers (Poster 4). *Jiaao Liu, University of California - Los Angeles*
5. Analyzing Multimodal Dialogic Inquiry in Virtual-Lab-Supported Physics Classrooms (Poster 5). *Luwei Bai, University of Cambridge*
6. Bayesian Bias-Aware Network Psychometrics (Poster 6). *Fatih Ozkan, Baylor University*
7. Becoming a Fulbright Foreign Student: Narratives of Participants from Kazakhstan (Poster 7). *Anarbek Yelshibayev, College of William & Mary*
8. Between Books and Babies: A Narrative Autoethnographic Study of an International Graduate Student Mother (Poster 8). *Barbara Mensah, University of Alabama*
9. Clustering Daily Routines with Image Processing: Revealing Behavioral Structures from EMA and Time Use Data (Poster 9). *Binhui Chen, Georgetown University; Qiwei He, Georgetown University; Margaret Kerr, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Heather Kirkorian, University of Wisconsin; McCall Booth, Georgetown University; Rachel Barr, Georgetown University*
10. Collecting Quantitative Sources of Validity Evidence for Self-Concept and Situational Interest Scales in College Mathematics (Poster 10). *Abel Sekone, San Diego State University*
11. Community, Culture, and Media Literacy: Supporting International Students' Adjustment in an ESL Classroom (Poster 11). *Esra Oz Cetindere, University of Cincinnati*
12. Embodiment: A Bifold Arts-Based Investigation into Academic Identity Experienced by a Chinese Doctoral

- Student (Poster 12). *Jialu Fan, University of Minnesota, Twin Cities*
13. Examining Nonresponse Patterns in GMAT Registration Data and Their Associations with Test Performance (Poster 13). *Yuxi Shen, Georgetown University; Kyung Chris T. Han, The Graduate Management Admission Council; Qiwei He, Georgetown University*
 14. From Hurt to Healing: Investigating the Relationship of Self-Regulation Strategies with the Psychological Impact of Cyberbullying (Poster 14). *Mehjabin Bhuiyan, University of Oklahoma; Huiting Zhou, University of Oklahoma; Benjamin C. Heddy, University of Oklahoma*
 15. From Meta-Analysis to Practice: Understanding How Education Research is Interpreted and Applied (Poster 15). *Hannah F. Scarbrough, Georgia State University*
 16. Historic Silences, Future Voices: Reconstructing Disability and Accommodation in Graduate Education (Poster 16). *Juliana Hirn, University of Central Florida; Amanda Elizabeth Evans, University of Central Florida; Audra Skukauskaitė, University of Central Florida*
 17. Measuring Relational Dynamics in Early Childhood Consultation: Alignment in Collaboration, Engagement, and Coaching Alliance (Poster 17). *Kaela Madison Tidus, University of Virginia; Jason Downer, University of Virginia; Rebecca Bulotsky-Shearer, University of Miami; Virginia E. Vitiello, University of Virginia; Bella S. Lerner, University of Miami; Amanda Paige Williford, University of Virginia*
 18. Nurturing Ecological Empathy: Pedagogical Approaches from the US, Italy, Germany, and Ecuador (Poster 18). *AnnaLise Hoopes, University of California - Los Angeles*
 19. Profiles of learning in STEM: The interplay of self-regulated learning, motivation, self-efficacy, and academic achievement (Poster 19). *Morgan A. Jernigan, Washington State University; Kira J. Carbonneau, Washington State University*
 20. Structuring Subjective Task Value: A Comparison of Correlated-Factors, Higher-Order, and Bifactor Models (Poster 20). *Qingqing Zhou, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Jessica R. Gladstone, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*
 21. Transition Experience of First-Year Chinese International Students in the U.S. Higher Education: A Qualitative Multiple-case Study (Poster 21). *Hongyan Wang, Binghamton University - SUNY*
 22. Using Student Behavior and Scores to Model Not Reached Items Due to Time Limits (Poster 22). *Samyukta Vakkalanka, Georgetown University; Qiwei He, Georgetown University*
 23. Variable Selection in Multilevel Models (Poster 23). *Siyao Du, University of Texas at Austin; Man Chen, University of Texas at Austin*
 24. Visualizing Membership Categorization Analysis in Contraceptive Commercials (Poster 24). *Katie Haus, Indiana University*

25. Voices from the Classroom: Indonesian Teachers' Narratives of Teaching Students with Disabilities (Poster 25). *Ikfina Maufuriyah, Indiana University*
 26. Working While Studying: How Does Student Employment Influence College Student Engagement (Poster 26). *Yiping Wang, University of California - Los Angeles*
- Chairs: *Apala Biswas, University of Cincinnati; Daniel O. Oyeniran, University of Alabama*

79.077-2. Teachers' Lives, Identities, and Journeys - Division K Section 3. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 3:45-5:15pm

Posters:

27. Collaborative Reflection in Teacher Education: A Duoethnographic Approach to Enriching Educators' Experiences (Poster 27). *Seoyeon Lee, University at Buffalo - SUNY*
28. Designated Identity Narratives: Teacher Philosophy Statements in Critical CS Education (Poster 28). *Brendan R. Henrique, University of California - Berkeley*
29. Reclaiming Histories and Reworlding Futures through an Ontological Commitment to Engaged Pedagogy and Holistic Praxis (Poster 29). *Yu-Chi Micki Lin, University of California - Riverside*
30. Teaching from Remembering: Collective Memories of Childhood as Pedagogical Resource and Risk (Poster 30). *Roni Barsoum, University of Michigan; Natalie R. Davis, University of Michigan*

79.077-3. Motivating and Motivated: Experiences, Contexts, and Socializers. SIG-Motivation in Education Cosponsored with Division C - Learning and Instruction; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 3:45-5:15pm

Posters:

31. Academic Freedom as a Psychological Resource: A Mixed-Method Study Across Three Countries (Poster 31). *Martin Daumiller, Ludwig Maximilian University of Munich; Johanna Maria Ott, University of Augsburg; mathangi ramasubramanian, University of Augsburg; Andrew Frein, University of Augsburg; Ronja Steinhauser, University of Mannheim; Stefan Janke, University of Mannheim; Oliver Dickhäuser, University of Mannheim; Markus Dresel, University of Augsburg*
32. Autonomy versus Competence for Learning and Creativity (Poster 32). *Sinan Akalin, University of Georgia; Emily Quinn Rosenzweig, Teachers College, Columbia University*
33. Basic Needs Insecurity and Belonging Among STEM Community College Students (Poster 33). *Stacy J. Priniski, Temple University; Renu Kumar, Minneapolis College; Leanne Davis, University of Washington; MG Hodge, Temple University; Renny Osuna Perla, Temple University;*

Jennifer Michelle Johnson, Temple University

34. Collective Connections: Predictors and Outcomes of Relatedness Consensus in Large-Lecture Classrooms (Poster 34). *Cole D. Johnson, McGill University; Johana Sava, McGill University; Sanheeta Shankar, McGill University; Romane Monnet, McGill University; Jessica Hunter, McGill University; Marianne Dubé, McGill University; Kristy A. Robinson, McGill University*
35. Exploring Teacher and Staff Self-efficacy Towards Trauma-Informed Practices: Findings From a Research-Practice Partnership (Poster 35). *Margaret K. Powers, Washington University in St. Louis; Megumi Grace Hine, Washington University in St. Louis; Erica Ellsworth Miller, Washington University in St. Louis; Sophie C. Song, Washington University in St. Louis; Sharonica Hardin-Bartley, St. Louis Research Practice Collaborative*
36. Fear of Failure: A Multilevel Exploration of the Individual and Contextual Effects (Poster 36). *Yikang Chen, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Ronnel B. King, Chinese University of Hong Kong*
37. Moderating Role of Competence in Parental Achievement Pressure and Achievement Goals (Poster 37). *Moonbee Kang, Korea National University of Education; Juyeon Song, Korea National University of Education; Woogul Lee, Korea National University of Education*
38. Need-Supportive Teaching in Chinese Vocational High School English Classrooms: Teachers' Perceptions and Practices (Poster 38). *Xiaorong Zhang, George Mason University; Alexandra Patzak, George Mason University*
39. Perceived Teacher Support and Student Motivation in Math and Science: The Moderating Role of School Type and Socioeconomic Status (Poster 39). *Haofei Li, The Ohio State University*
40. Teachers' Evaluation and Reporting Orientations and their Impact on Elementary Students' Motivation (Poster 40). *Melissa Lefebvre, University of New Hampshire*

79.077-4. Experiential Education and Community Engagement: Scholarship and Practice Poster Session 2. SIG-Experiential Education and Community Engagement: Scholarship and Practice; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 3:45-5:15pm

Poster:

41. Generative Knowing: Learning from Experiences Differently (Poster 41). *Younghyun Kim, University of Georgia; Aliko Nicolaidis, University of Georgia; Trisha Barefield, Kansas State University; Ahreum Lim, Arizona State University; Shannon Perry, Valdosta State University*

79.078. e-Lightning Ed-Talk Session 19 - Stage 1. AERA e-Lightning Ed-Talks; AERA Ed Talk
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Exhibit Hall A - Stage 1; 3:45-5:15pm

Participants:

- Designated Identity Narratives: Teacher Philosophy Statements in Critical CS Education (Stage 1, 3:50 PM). *Brendan R. Henrique, University of California - Berkeley*
- Basic Needs Insecurity and Belonging Among STEM Community College Students (Stage 1, 3:59 PM). *Stacy J. Priniski, Temple University; Renu Kumar, Minneapolis College; Leanne Davis, University of Washington; MG Hodge, Temple University; Renny Osuna Perla, Temple University; Jennifer Michelle Johnson, Temple University*
- Exploring Teacher and Staff Self-efficacy Towards Trauma-Informed Practices: Findings From a Research-Practice Partnership (Stage 1, 4:08 PM). *Margaret K. Powers, Washington University in St. Louis; Megumi Grace Hine, Washington University in St. Louis; Erica Ellsworth Miller, Washington University in St. Louis; Sophie C. Song, Washington University in St. Louis; Sharonica Hardin-Bartley, St. Louis Research Practice Collaborative*
- Perceived Teacher Support and Student Motivation in Math and Science: The Moderating Role of School Type and Socioeconomic Status (Stage 1, 4:26 PM). *Haofei Li, The Ohio State University*
- Teachers' Evaluation and Reporting Orientations and their Impact on Elementary Students' Motivation (Stage 1, 4:35 PM). *Melissa Lefebvre, University of New Hampshire*
- Generative Knowing: Learning from Experiences Differently (Stage 1, 4:44 PM). *Younghyun Kim, University of Georgia; Aliko Nicolaidis, University of Georgia; Trisha Barefield, Kansas State University; Ahreum Lim, Arizona State University; Shannon Perry, Valdosta State University*
- Chair: *Reinhard Pekrun, University of Essex*

Saturday, April 11th, 5:00 pm

80.010. Ball State University Teachers College Reception.
Affiliated Groups; Reception
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 6th Floor, Metropolitan; 5:00-7:00pm

Saturday, April 11th, 5:45 pm

Division Sessions

81.010. Division D Business Meeting. Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Business Meeting
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Wilshire Grand Ballroom I; 5:45-6:45pm
Chair: *Jessica Nina Lester, Indiana University*

81.011. Division I Business Meeting. Division I - Education in

the Professions; Business Meeting
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum
G; 5:45-6:45pm

Chair: *Linette P. Ross, National Board of Medical Examiners*
Co-Chairs: *Violet Kulo, University of Maryland - Baltimore;*
Yuane Jia, Rutgers University

SIG Sessions

81.012. Access, Detracking & Tracking SIG Business Meeting.

SIG-Access, Detracking, and Tracking; Business Meeting
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum
B; 5:45-6:45pm

Chair: *Constance Clark, Rutgers University - Newark*

81.013. Accreditation, Assessment, and Program Evaluation in Education Preparation SIG Business Meeting.

SIG-Accreditation, Assessment, and Program Evaluation in
Education Preparation; Business Meeting
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Los
Feliz; 5:45-6:45pm

Chair: *Todd McCardle, Eastern Kentucky University*
Officers: *Kimberly Jamison, University of North Carolina -*
Wilmington; Ruchi Bhatnagar, Georgia State University

81.014. Asian Americans and Pacific Islanders in Education and Research SIG Business Meeting.

SIG-Asian Americans and Pacific Islanders in Education and Research;
Business Meeting
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304A;
5:45-6:45pm

Chair: *Yinying Wang, Georgia State University*
Officers: *Lei Jiang, University of Kansas; Kevin M. Wong,*
Pepperdine University; Wenyang Sun, University of Utah;
Khánh Lê, Queens College - CUNY

81.015. Biographical and Documentary Research SIG Business Meeting.

SIG-Biographical and Documentary Research;
Business Meeting
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 306A;
5:45-6:45pm

Chair: *Margaret-Mary Sulentic Dowell, Louisiana State University*

81.016. Annual Business Meeting: Bourdieu in Educational Research SIG.

SIG-Bourdieu in Educational Research;
Business Meeting
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304C;
5:45-6:45pm

Chair: *Frederick de Moll, Bielefeld University*

81.017. Career & Technical Education and Workplace Learning Annual Business Meeting.

SIG-Career &

Technical Education and Workplace Learning; Business
Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, San Gabriel B; 5:45-
6:45pm

Chair: *Walter G. Ecton, University of Michigan*

81.018. CASE Business Meeting.

SIG-Caribbean and African
Studies in Education; Business Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Level 3, Santa Monica B; 5:45-6:45pm

Chair: *Alicia Francisca Noreiga, Acadia University*

81.019. Catholic Education SIG Business Meeting.

SIG-Catholic Education; Business Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Palos Verdes; 5:45-
6:45pm

Chair: *John L. Beltramo, Santa Clara University*

81.020. Classroom Assessment SIG Business Meeting and Networking Session.

SIG-Classroom Assessment; Business
Meeting
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 6th Floor, Palace;
5:45-6:45pm

Chair: *Dustin Sonny James Van Orman, Western Washington*
University
Officers: *Erin E. Riley-Lepo, The College of New Jersey; Divya*
Varier, George Mason University

81.021. Classroom Management SIG Business Meeting.

SIG-Classroom Management; Business Meeting
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Georgia II;
5:45-6:45pm

Chairs: *Dorothy E. Hines, University of Kansas; Nicholas E.*
Mitchell, University of Kansas

81.022. Invited Symposium: One World, One Family: Constructing a New Vision of Education from the Asian Philosophical Perspective.

SIG-Confucianism, Taoism,
Buddhism and Education; Business Meeting
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 501B;
5:45-6:45pm

Chair: *Dengting Boyanton, Sino-American Educational Research*
Association
Speakers: *Gerard Postiglione, University of Hong Kong; Jing Lin,*
University of Maryland; Xin Li, California State University -
Long Beach; Mark L. Blum, University of California -
Berkeley; Jin Jr Shi, Dharma Realm Buddhist University;
Maung Ting Nyeu, University of California - Santa Barbara;
Dengting Boyanton, Sino-American Educational Research
Association

Discussants: *Liz Jackson, University of Hong Kong; Jason Cong*
Lin, The Education University of Hong Kong

Officer: *Wenjin Guo, Xi'an University of Architecture and*
Technology

81.023. Critical Educators for Social Justice (CESJ) SIG Business Meeting and Reception. SIG-Critical Educators for Social Justice; Business Meeting
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 301A;
5:45-6:45pm

Chair: *Shamaine Bertrand, The College of New Jersey*

81.024. Critical Examination of Race, Ethnicity, Class, and Gender: Business Meeting, Awards Ceremony, and Reception. SIG-Critical Examination of Race, Ethnicity, Class and Gender in Education; Business Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Beaudry A; 5:45-6:45pm

Chair: *Janice A. Byrd, Pennsylvania State University*

Co-Chairs: *Jemimah L. Young, Texas A&M University; Rossina Zamora Liu, University of Maryland*

Speaker: *Carmen Kynard, Texas Christian University*

Officers: *Blake O'Neal Turner, Marquette University; Alexis Morgan Young, Michigan State University; Andrea A. Joseph-McCatty, University of Tennessee; LaWanda W. Ward, Pennsylvania State University*

81.025. SIG Critical Peace Education Business Meeting. SIG-Critical Peace Education; Business Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Santa Anita A; 5:45-6:45pm

Chair: *Raul Olmo Fregoso Bailón, University of Nevada - Reno*

81.026. (Re)committing to Justice-Oriented Praxis: Unforgetting Histories and Imagining Futures in Early Childhood Education. SIG-Critical Perspectives on Early Childhood Education; Business Meeting
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 309;
5:45-7:15pm

Chair: *Oona Fontanella-Nothom, California State University - Dominguez Hills*

Officers: *Nathaniel Bryan, University of Texas at Austin; Allison Sterling Henward, Pennsylvania State University; Tiffany Rowland, University of Toledo; Ruby Batz, University of Nevada - Reno; Stephanie C. Sanders-Smith, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Alisha Nguyen, Lesley University; David Vining, Columbia Greenhouse Nursery School*

81.027. Critical Posthuman and Postfoundational Studies Business Meeting. SIG-Critical Posthuman and Postfoundational Studies in Education; Business Meeting
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 7;
5:45-6:45pm

Chair: *Kathryn J. Strom, California State University - East Bay*

Officers: *Sophia Jeong, The Ohio State University; Allyson V. Compton, Iona University; Saralyn McKinnon-Crowley, Baylor University*

81.028. Business Meeting with the Cultural-Historical Research SIG. SIG-Cultural-Historical Research; Business Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Santa Barbara C; 5:45-6:45pm

Chair: *Shirin Vossoughi, Northwestern University*

Co-Chair: *Peter Hick, Edge Hill University*

Officers: *Sharon Chang, Teachers College, Columbia University; Na Lor, Teachers College, Columbia University; Yehyang Lee, Syracuse University; Karlyn R. Adams-Wiggins, Portland State University*

81.029. Business Meeting: Data-Driven Decision Making SIG 179. SIG-Data-Driven Decision Making in Education; Business Meeting
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum H; 5:45-6:45pm

Chair: *Kara Lasater, University of Arkansas at Fayetteville*

Participants: *Jennifer L. Kobrin, University of Kansas; Jo Beth Jimerson, Texas Christian University; Vincent Cho, Boston College; Kevin Fortner, Georgia State University*

81.030. Districts in Research and Reform Business Meeting. SIG-Districts in Research & Reform; Business Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, La Brea; 5:45-6:45pm
Chairs: *Debbie Kim, NORC at the University of Chicago; Jennifer R. Cowhy, University of Arkansas; Amanda Slaten Frasier, East Tennessee State University; Abigail Stein, Carnegie Mellon University*

Participants: *Daniel Dawer, University of Texas at Austin; Elisabeth Kim, Lehman College*

81.031. Educational Change SIG Business Meeting. SIG-Educational Change; Business Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Level 3, Santa Monica D; 5:45-6:45pm
Chair: *Patricia M. Virella, Montclair State University*
Moderator: *Taeyeon Kim, University of Nebraska - Lincoln; Lauren P. Bailes, University of Delaware*

81.032. Elliot Eisner SIG Business Meeting. SIG-Elliot Eisner; Business Meeting
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 306B;
5:45-6:45pm
Chair: *Jennifer Bartee, University of the District of Columbia*

81.033. Faculty Teaching, Evaluation, and Development Business Meeting. SIG-Faculty Teaching, Evaluation, and Development; Business Meeting
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum I;
5:45-6:45pm
Chair: *Lisa A Lambert Snodgrass, Purdue University*

- 81.034. Fiscal Issues, Policy, and Education Finance SIG Business Meeting.** SIG-Fiscal Issues, Policy and Education Finance; Business Meeting
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 9; 5:45-6:45pm
Chair: *David S. Knight, University of Washington*
Co-Chair: *David G. Martinez, University of South Carolina*
- 81.035. Improvement Science SIG Business Meeting: Connect and Reflect on the Future of Improvement Research.** SIG-Improvement Science in Education; Business Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, San Gabriel A; 5:45-6:45pm
Chair: *Elizabeth Zumpe, University of Oklahoma*
- 81.036. Informal Learning Environments Research (ILER) Business Meeting.** SIG-Informal Learning Environment Research; Business Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Santa Anita B; 5:45-6:45pm
Chair: *Camellia Sanford-Dolly, Rockman et al Cooperative*
Officers: *Kieren Rende Mendoza, University of Nebraska - Omaha; Kimberly Reynolds Kelly, California State University - Long Beach; Lynne Zummo, University of Utah; Deneen S. Dixon-Payne, Towson University; Kristina M. Stamatis, University of Nebraska Omaha; Megan Ennes, University of Florida*
- 81.037. Leadership for School Improvement SIG Business Meeting.** SIG-Leadership for School Improvement; Business Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, San Bernardino; 5:45-6:45pm
Chair: *Alison Wilson, University of Houston*
- 81.038. Leadership for Social Justice SIG Business Meeting.** SIG-Leadership for Social Justice; Business Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Level 2, Echo Park; 5:45-6:45pm
Chair: *Leslie Ann Locke, Minnesota State University - Mankato*
Participants: *Liliana E. Castrellon, San José State University; Mario Jackson, Florida State University; Amaarah N. DeCuir, American University; Shannon Holder, Central Connecticut State University; Vajra M. Watson, University of Redlands; Lok-Sze Wong, University of North Texas; LaSonja Roberts, Western Michigan University; Rebecca J. Lowenhaupt, Boston College; Zakiya Stewart, Empathy's Edge Consulting; Raketa Ouedraogo-Thomas, University of North Carolina - Charlotte*
- 81.039. Learning and Teaching in Educational Leadership (LTEL) SIG Business Meeting.** SIG-Learning and Teaching in Educational Leadership; Business Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, San Gabriel C; 5:45-6:45pm
Chair: *Erin Anderson, University of Denver*
- 81.040. Constructing New Visions for Literature Research.** SIG-Literature; Business Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Los Cerritos; 5:45-6:45pm
Chair: *Selena E Van Horn, California State University - Fresno*
Officers: *Scott Storm, University at Albany - SUNY; Kelly K. Wissman, University at Albany - SUNY*
- 81.041. Middle Level Education Research (MLER) Business Meeting.** SIG-Middle-Level Education Research; Business Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Los Feliz; 5:45-6:45pm
Chair: *Lisa M Harrison, Ohio University*
- 81.042. Montessori Education SIG Business Meeting.** SIG-Montessori Education; Business Meeting
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum J; 5:45-6:45pm
Chair: *Brooke Culclasure, Furman University*
- 81.043. Motivation in Education SIG Business Meeting.** SIG-Motivation in Education; Business Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Level 3, Avalon; 5:45-6:45pm
Chair: *Jason A. Chen, College of William & Mary*
Officers: *Pei Pei Liu, Colby College; Kristy A. Robinson, McGill University; Martinique Ann Sealy Mitchell, Virginia Commonwealth University; Shelbi Laura Kuhlmann, University of Memphis; So Yeon Lee, The University of Alabama at Birmingham; Sanheeta Shankar, McGill University; Wonjoon Cha, The Ohio State University*
- 81.044. Narrative Research SIG Business Meeting - Come join us!** SIG-Narrative Research; Business Meeting
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 1; 5:45-6:45pm
Chair: *Min Wang, SUNY New Paltz*
Co-Chair: *Leia K. Cain, University of Tennessee*
Officers: *Leslie M. Gauna, University of Houston - Clear Lake; Zachary Schafer, University of Nebraska - Lincoln; Amy L. Boniface, Maricopa Community Colleges*
- 81.045. Online Teaching and Learning SIG Business Meeting.** SIG-Online Teaching and Learning; Business Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, San Fernando; 5:45-6:45pm
Chair: *Rebecca M. Quintana, University of Michigan*
Officers: *Julie Brockman Smart, Anderson University; Jacob M. Aguinaga, University of Michigan; Jolie V. Kennedy, Empire State University - SUNY*

Panelists: *Mary F. Rice, University of New Mexico; Patrick R. Lowenthal, Boise State University; Daniela Castellanos-Reyes, North Carolina State University; Peter Shea, University at Albany - SUNY; Larisa A. Olesova, University of Florida*

81.046. Open Scholarship SIG Business Meeting. SIG-Open Scholarship; Business Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Santa Barbara A; 5:45-6:45pm

Chair: *Matthew C. Makel, University of Calgary*
Participants: *D. Betsy Mccoach, University of Connecticut; Sondra Stegenga, University of Utah*

81.047. Organizational Theory SIG Business Meeting: Imagining Organizational Theory as a Tool of Resistance and Hope. SIG-Organizational Theory; Business Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Santa Barbara B; 5:45-6:45pm

Chair: *Jose Eos Trinidad, University of California - Berkeley*

81.048. Portfolios and Reflection in Teaching and Teacher Education SIG Business Meeting. SIG-Portfolios and Reflection in Teaching and Teacher Education; Business Meeting
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Plaza II; 5:45-6:45pm

Chair: *Nathan E. Bell, American Educational Research Association*

81.049. Empathy in problem, project, and invention learning environments. SIG-Problem-Based and Project-Based Learning; Business Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Santa Anita C; 5:45-6:45pm

Chair: *Audra Skukauskaite, University of Central Florida*
Discussant: *Emily Adah Miller, University of Georgia*
Panelists: *Daniel Edelen, Georgia State University; Stephanie Couch, Massachusetts Institute of Technology*

81.050. Qualitative Research SIG Business Meeting and Reception. SIG-Qualitative Research; Business Meeting
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 7th Floor, Hollywood Ballroom I; 5:45-7:45pm

Chair: *Jennifer R. Wolgemuth, University of South Florida*
Co-Chairs: *Shena Sanchez, University of Alabama; Meagan Call-Cummings, Johns Hopkins University*

81.051. Queer Studies SIG Business Meeting. SIG-Queer Studies; Business Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Beaudry B; 5:45-6:45pm
Chair: *Angel D. Gonzalez, California State University - Fresno*
Officers: *Jarrel T. Johnson, University of Utah; Quortne R.*

Hutchings, Northern Illinois University

81.052. Research Focus on Education and Sport SIG Business Meeting. SIG-Research Focus on Education and Sport; Business Meeting

Westin Bonaventure, Level 2, Mt. Washington; 5:45-6:45pm
Chair: *Sarah E. Stokowski, Clemson University*
Participants: *Molly P. Harry, University of Florida; Ezinne Ofoegbu, Santa Clara University*

81.053. SIG-RME & SIG-SIMS Joint Business Meeting & Reception. SIG-Research in Mathematics Education
Cospponsored with SIG-Socio-Political Issues in Mathematics and Science Education; Business Meeting
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum C; 5:45-6:45pm

Chairs: *Karen L. Terrell, Loyola University Maryland; Grace A. Chen, New York University*
Co-Chair: *Erica Litke, University of Delaware*
Speaker: *Rochelle Gutierrez, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Officers: *Charles E. Wilkes, University of California - Davis; Patricia Buenrostro, University of Illinois at Chicago; Robyn K. Pinilla, University of Texas - El Paso; Melissa A. Gallagher, U.S. Math Recovery Council; Carlos Nicolas Gómez Marchant, University of Texas at Austin; Lauren Rigby, University of Texas at Austin; Maria Maria Castillo, Vanderbilt University; Daniel Morales-Doyle, University of Illinois at Chicago; Mallika Scott, California State University - Fullerton*

81.054. 2025-2026 Research on Teacher Induction SIG Business Meeting. SIG-Research on Teacher Induction; Business Meeting
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Georgia I; 5:45-6:45pm

Participant: *Amanda S. Mayeaux, University of Louisiana at Lafayette*

81.055. Rural Education SIG Business Meeting. SIG-Rural Education; Business Meeting
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 10; 5:45-6:45pm

Chair: *Catharine Biddle, University of Maine*
Officers: *Sara Lohrman Hartman, Ohio University; Daniella Hall Sutherland, University of Vermont; Kessa Roberts, Clemson University; Ty C. McNamee, University of Kentucky*

81.056. School-University Partnership Research SIG Business Meeting. SIG-School-University Partnership Research; Business Meeting
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 2; 5:45-6:45pm

Chair: *Jori S. Beck, College of William & Mary*
Officers: *Melissa A. Baker, Abraham Baldwin Agricultural College; Morgan Faison, University of Georgia*

81.057. AERA Second Language Research (SLR) SIG Business Meeting. SIG-Second Language Research; Business Meeting
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 3; 5:45-7:15pm

Chair: *Kongji Qin, New York University*
Co-Chair: *Christine Montecillo Leider, University of Massachusetts - Lowell*

Panelists: *Matt DeRoo, Florida International University; Shuzhan Li, Ithaca College; Caitlin G. Fine, Metropolitan State University of Denver; Golnar Fotouhi, University of Massachusetts - Lowell; Xinhang Hermione Hu, University of Maryland; David González Nieto, Northern Illinois University*

81.058. Business Meeting - Social Studies Research SIG. SIG-Social Studies Research; Business Meeting
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum F; 5:45-6:45pm

Chair: *Timothy Monreal, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

81.059. Special and Inclusive Education Research SIG Business Meeting. SIG-Special and Inclusive Education Research; Business Meeting
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Atrium II; 5:45-7:15pm

Chair: *Jessica Ann McQueston, Sam Houston State University*
Co-Chair: *Chelsea Tracy-Bronson, Stockton University*
Officer: *Nickie Coomer, Colorado College*

81.060. Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis SIG Business Meeting. SIG-Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis; Business Meeting
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Echo Park; 5:45-6:45pm

Chairs: *Carlton J. Fong, Texas State University; Derek Rodgers, University of Iowa*

Officers: *Mariola Moeyaert, University at Albany - SUNY; Amanda Neitzel, Johns Hopkins University; Bixi Zhang, Graduate Center - CUNY; Jihyun Lee, University of North Texas; Xue Wang, Johns Hopkins University*

81.061. The Legacy of Dr. A. Wade Boykin's Talent Development SIG. SIG-Talent Development of Students Placed at Risk; Business Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Level 3, Santa Monica C; 5:45-6:45pm
Chair: *Ashley Griffin Gilchrist, Bowie State University*

81.062. Structures to Elevate Practitioner Voice: The TAR SIG

Mission. SIG-Teacher as Researcher; Business Meeting
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 6; 5:45-6:45pm

Chair: *Kevin Cataldo, Newark Board of Education/Montclair State University*

Officers: *Kierstin M. Giunco, University of Cincinnati; Lisa Rose Johnson, Old Dominion University*

81.063. Teaching Educational Psychology Business Meeting. SIG-Teaching Educational Psychology; Business Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, La Cienega; 5:45-6:45pm

Chair: *Lisa D. Bendixen, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*
Co-Chair: *Susanne Narciss, Technische Universitaet Dresden*

81.064. Teaching History SIG Business Meeting. SIG-Teaching History; Business Meeting
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum A; 5:45-6:45pm

Chair: *Brittany Jones, University at Buffalo - SUNY*
Officer: *Jenni Conrad, Oregon State University*

81.065. SIG Technology as an Agent of Change in Teaching and Learning Business Meeting. SIG-Technology as an Agent of Change in Teaching and Learning; Business Meeting
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 8; 5:45-6:45pm

Chair: *Bret Staudt Willet, Florida State University*
Co-Chairs: *Ai-Chu Elisha Ding, University of Georgia; Matthew L. Wilson, Kennesaw State University*
Officers: *Yin Hong Cheah, University of Idaho; Lauren Bagdy, University of Georgia; Lauren Weisberg, University of Texas - Arlington; Kristin Hemingway, Georgia State University; Nazanin Adhami, University of Florida*

81.066. Technology, Instruction, Cognition, and Learning (TICL) Business Meeting and Reception. SIG-Technology, Instruction, Cognition & Learning; Business Meeting
Westin Bonaventure, Level 2, Beverly; 5:45-6:45pm

Chair: *Victoria Lynn Lowell, Purdue University*
Officers: *Ayesha Sadaf, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Meina Zhu, Wayne State University; Peng He, Washington State University; Fan Xu, N/A; Qin Xie, University of Minnesota*

Saturday, April 11th, 6:00 pm

Division Sessions

82.010. Division J Graduate Student Reception. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Reception
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Plaza III;
6:00-7:00pm

82.011. Temple University College of Education and Human Development Reception. Affiliated Groups; Reception
Westin Bonaventure, Level 3, Hollywood Ballroom; 6:00-8:00pm

82.012. The University of Texas at Austin Reception. Affiliated Groups; Reception
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum D; 6:00-8:00pm

82.013. University of Virginia School of Education and Human Development Reception. Affiliated Groups; Reception
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Atrium III;
6:00-8:00pm

Saturday, April 11th, 6:30 pm

83.010. University of California System Colleges of Education Reception. Affiliated Groups; Reception
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 403A;
6:30-8:30pm

Saturday, April 11th, 6:45 pm

Committee Sessions

84.010. Graduate Student Social. Graduate Student Council; Reception
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 502B;
6:45-8:15pm
Participants: *Cammie Justus-Smith, Virginia Commonwealth University; Edith P. Middleton, Teachers College, Columbia University; Marjorie M. Hahn, Stanford University; Mark Wilson, University of Houston*

Division Sessions

84.011. Joint Social Reception: Divisions D & H and SIGs Critical Quantitative Methodologies, Data-Driven Decision Making, Qualitative Research, and Survey Research in Education. Division H - Research, Evaluation and Assessment in Schools Cosponsored with Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies, SIG-Critical

Quantitative Methodologies, SIG-Data-Driven Decision Making in Education, SIG-Open Scholarship and SIG-Qualitative Research, SIG-Survey Research in Education; Reception
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Wilshire Grand Ballroom II; 6:45-8:45pm

SIG Sessions

84.012. Joint Reception: Leadership for School Improvement SIG, Educational Change SIG, Organizational Theory SIG, Systems Thinking in Education SIG. SIG-Leadership for School Improvement Cosponsored with SIG-Educational Change and SIG-Organizational Theory, SIG-Systems Thinking in Education; Reception
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Santa Anita A; 6:45-8:15pm

Participants: *Jose Eos Trinidad, University of California - Berkeley; Alison Wilson, University of Houston; Taeyeon Kim, University of Nebraska - Lincoln; Lok-Sze Wong, University of North Texas; Kate Kennedy, University of Cincinnati; Maxwell Yurkofsky, Radford University; Samantha L. Viano, George Mason University; Patricia M. Virella, Montclair State University; Whitney M. Hegseth, University of La Verne*

84.013. Just Education Policy Fellows Reception. Affiliated Groups; Reception
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 504;
6:45-8:15pm

Chair: *Janelle T. Scott, University of California - Berkeley*

Saturday, April 11th, 7:00 pm

Division Sessions

85.010. Division I Social (Division I Members Only - Pre-registration required with chairs). Division I - Education in the Professions; Reception
Lazy Dog LA Live , 800 W Olympic Blvd. #a-180, Los Angeles, CA 90015, Restaurant; 7:00-9:00pm
Chairs: *Linette P. Ross, National Board of Medical Examiners; Violet Kulo, University of Maryland - Baltimore; Yuane Jia, Rutgers University*

85.011. California State University System Colleges of Education Reception. Affiliated Groups; Reception
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Wilshire Grand Ballroom III; 7:00-9:00pm

85.012. Faculty of Education and Human Development, The Education University of Hong Kong Reception. Affiliated Groups; Reception
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum E;
7:00-10:00pm

85.013. Spencer Foundation Reception. Affiliated Groups; Reception
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 4 and 5; 7:00-10:00pm

85.014. University of Kansas & Kansas State University Reception. Affiliated Groups; Reception
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Atrium I;
7:00-9:00pm

Saturday, April 11th, 7:30 pm

SIG Sessions

86.010. Access, Detracking, and Tracking SIG and Leadership for Social Justice SIG Joint Reception. SIG-Access, Detracking, and Tracking Cosponsored with SIG-Leadership for Social Justice; Reception
The Los Angeles Athletic Club, The Los Angeles Athletic Club; 7:30-10:00pm
Chair: *Constance Clark, Rutgers University - Newark*

Wednesday, April 8th, 7:45 am

Division Sessions

87.010. Division A - Section 1: Leadership Virtual Poster Session. Division A - Administration; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

School Leadership Effect on Student Achievement Through Teacher Trust: A Meta-Structural Equation Modeling Approach. *Jingping Sun, University of Alabama; Junqi Lin, University of Alabama*

Who's Minding the Teachers? Principal Practices That Support Teacher Well-Being in High-Poverty Schools. *Diana Sierra, Florida Atlantic University; Patricia Maslin-Ostrowski, Florida Atlantic University*

Lessons Learned from the Pandemic to Inform Decision-Making About AI in K-12 Schools. *Andrea Cutt, University of Rochester; David E. Miller, University of Rochester;*

Raffaella Borasi, University of Rochester; Zenon Borys, University of Rochester

A Phenomenological Study of Black Female School Administrators and their Stories of Leadership. *Tommy Wells, Bellarmine University; Vanessa Gee, Indiana University - Purdue University at Indianapolis*

The Emotional Weight of Leadership: Understanding Principals' Worry. *Peleg Dor-Haim, Tel Aviv University*
Sustainable Spirit: A Case Study of Whole Child Reform Cultivating Wisdom, Courage, Compassion. *Diane Martindale, DePaul University*

Institutional Digital Leadership and ICT Competency: The Moderating Role of Teaching Experience in Chinese Universities. *Jing Cai, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia; Aida Hanim A Hamid, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia; Mohamed Yusoff Mohd Nor, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia*

PLCs and Teacher Satisfaction: Mediating Teacher Leadership Across School Types. *wang xueting, East China Normal University; Chen Xie, East China Normal University*
Getting into the Zone: School principals' work-related flow and its drivers and outcomes. *Junjun Chen, Education University of Hong Kong; Zan Li, The Education University of Hong Kong; Cheng Jin, The Education University of Hong Kong*

87.010. Division A - Section 4: School Contexts and Communities Virtual Poster Session. Division A - Administration; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Case Study of Family Engagement in Mathematics Education at a Local Middle School. *Esperanza Ochoa, San Diego State University*

87.010. Division B - Section 1: Cultural Inquiry in Curriculum Studies Virtual Poster Session. Division B - Curriculum Studies; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Curricular Erasure And Queer Invisibility: A Content Analysis Of Indian School Textbooks. *Nishtha Saxena, University of Delhi; Anya Aggarwal, University of Delhi*

87.010. Division B - Section 2: Exploring Past, Present, and Future Curricular Questions Virtual Poster Session. Division B - Curriculum Studies; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Still Waiting for Superman: A Curricular Retrospective of the No Child Left Behind Era. *Katherine A. Perrotta, Mercer University*

Cultural Memory, Race, and the Secondary English Canon.
Dorothea M. Anagnostopoulos, University of Connecticut;
Austin Jerrod Unowitz, University of Connecticut
Exploring and Teaching LGBTQ+ Labor Histories. *Adam I.*
Attwood, Austin Peay State University; *Niklaus Ryker K.*
Christensen, Austin Peay State University

87.010. Division B - Section 3: Theories, Methodologies, and Philosophies of Curriculum Studies Virtual Poster Session. Division B - Curriculum Studies; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Entanglement with the Hidden Curriculum of Grading. *Kirsten Robbins, SUNY - College at Oneonta;* *Ann Fradkin-Hayslip, SUNY - College at Oneonta*

87.010. Division B - Section 6: De/Colonization and Transformative Curriculum Studies Virtual Poster Session. Division B - Curriculum Studies; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

“And a take-apart seal in a pear tree...”: MACOS and Material Histories of Playful Pedagogies. *Nicole K. Weinberg, Texas Christian University*

87.010. Division C - Section 1a: Literacy Virtual Poster Session. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Parent and Student Perspectives on Writing and Literacy: Listening to Diverse Voices. *Roselyn Gishen*
Maternal Literacy Practices and Vocabulary Development in Preschool Children. *Anosha Islam, Air University;* *Lauren R. Franklin, Baby Talk Child Development Lab;* *Fizza Farrukh, Air University*

87.010. Division C - Section 1c: Mathematics Virtual Poster Session. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Unraveling the Psychological and Behavioral Dynamics of Classroom Improvement: Insights from TALIS Shanghai Data. *Weitong Liu, Shandong University;* *Yuxuan Yan, Shandong University;* *Xinwei Chang, University of Glasgow;* *Hui Zhang, Shandong University*

87.010. Division C - Section 1e: Engineering and Computer Science Virtual Poster Session. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Programming Learning Supported by Generative Artificial Intelligence: Student Programming Performance and Cognitive Load. *Heng Zhang, University of Hong Kong;* *Jing Zhang, Universiti Sains Malaysia*
Understanding Data Story Construction with a Narrative Comprehension Lens: Implications for Learning Design. *Jennifer Posada, University of Maryland - Baltimore County;* *Yetunde Okueso, University of Maryland - Baltimore County;* *Louise G. Yarnall, SRI International;* *Hui Yang, SRI International;* *Lujie Karen Chen, University of Maryland - Baltimore County*
Improving the Spatial Visualization Skills of College Engineering Students by Using an Explicit Instruction Approach. *Yi Ding, Fordham University;* *Qian Wang, New York University;* *Jiayi Wang, University of Houston;* *Qiong Yu, Queens College - CUNY*

87.010. Division C - Section 2a: Cognitive and Motivational Processes Virtual Poster Session. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Nature, Predictors, and Outcomes of Students' Motivation Profiles: A Longitudinal Person-Centered Approach. *Mouhamadou Thiam, Université de Moncton;* *Nicole Lirette-Pitre, University of Moncton*
The Relationship of Sources of Research Self-Efficacy Profiles with Research Outcome Expectancy and Self-Efficacy. *Leigh M. Harrell-Williams, University of Memphis;* *Eli Andrew Jones, University of Memphis;* *Luke Walden, Union University*
Linking Growth Mindset and Academic Coping to Grit and Self-Handicapping Behaviors in Neurodiverse Adolescents (Poster 10). *Rahma F. Goran, Temple University;* *Cabi Wang, Temple University;* *Jay Tarnoff, Immaculata University;* *Xu Jiang, Temple University*

87.010. Division C - Section 2b: Learning and Motivation in Social and Cultural Contexts Virtual Poster Session. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Is Translanguaging Universal? A Systematic Review Across Global Language Contexts. *Yueqing Zhong, George Mason*

University

Growth Mindset, Stress, & Test Anxiety in Middle School Students. *Eva M Lucignano, Rowan University; Tenelle Porter, Rowan University*

Post-COVID-19 Era: Improving Learning and Reducing Violence through Successful Educational Actions at a Brazilian School. *Roseli Rodrigue de Mello, University of Sao Carlos; Antonio Alvaro Soares Zuin, Universidade Federal de São Carlos; Bruno Cortegoso Prezenszky, Universidade Federal de São Carlos; Denise Bachega, University of San Carlos*

Bridging Theory and Practice: How AI Feedback Can Enhance Learning Assistants' Pedagogical Flexibility in STEM Classrooms. *Ramadhan Mubarak Hamisi, University of Colorado - Boulder*

87.010. Division C - Section 3a: Learning Environments

Virtual Poster Session. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Practitioner Perspectives on Public Speaking Education in K-12 Schools: An Implementation Science Approach. *Lauren Biegley, Lehigh University; Brook Sawyer, Lehigh University*

87.010. Division D - Section 1: Measurement, Psychometrics, and Assessment Virtual Poster Session.

Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Differential Item Functioning of Personal and Social Responsibility Questionnaire among School and University Students: An Application of Propensity Score-Based Multidimensional Item Response Theory. *Amal Alhadabi, Sultan Qaboos University*

A Large Language Model-Based Framework for Automated and Accurate Chinese Essay Evaluation. *Yana Xia, East China Normal University; Xiang Feng, East China Normal University*

Robust Estimation of 2PL IRT Parameters via Deep Learning under Non-Ideal Testing Conditions. *Yunbo Yang, University of Chicago*

Development of a Multidimensional Cognitive Ability CAT Using Neural Network Graded Modeling. *Wen Sun, Beijing University of Chinese Medicine; Zichen Liu, Beijing University of Chinese Medicine; Wenjie Xu, Beijing University of Chinese Medicine; Lei Quan, Beijing University of Chinese Medicine; Zongshuo Sha, Beijing University of Chinese Medicine; Yixing Liu, Beijing University of Chinese Medicine*

Deepening Understanding of Common Persons Design in Score Equating: A Simulation Study. *Jiayi Liu, Peking University; Zhehan Jiang, Peking University; Tianpeng Zheng, Peking University; Shicong Feng, Peking University*

Developing a Measure of Spiritual, Emotional, and Physical Dimensions of College Student Well-being. *Kim Proctor, California State University - Dominguez Hills*

Beyond the Noise: Uncovering the Effects of Careless Respondents in Cognitive Diagnostic Modeling. *Tugay Kaçak, Trakya University; Mehtap Aktaş, Trakya University*

From Past Debates to Future Visions: Modelling Generic Problem-Solving Competence in PISA 2012. *Lan Anh Nguyen Khoa, University of Melbourne; Mark R. Wilson, University of California - Berkeley; Cuc Thi Kim Nguyen, University of Melbourne; Matthew Gordon Ray Courtney, Nazarbayev University*

Validating an Instrument for Students' Personal Learning Device Acceptance, Use and Self-Directed Home-Based Learning. *Hwee Lee Seah, MOE; Choon Lang Quek, National Institute of Education, Nanyang Technological University*

87.010. Division D - Section 2: Statistical Theory and Quantitative Methods Virtual Poster Session.

Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Understanding Burnout Among Korean Elementary School Teachers: A Post-Selection Inference Analysis. *SUNGMIN LEE, Korea National University of Education; Jin Eun Yoo, Korea National University of Education*

Evolving Themes in Educational Research: A Structural Topic Modeling of AERA Journals. *Nurcan Kahraman, Bursa Uludag University; Rumeysa Beyazhancer, Bursa Uludag University*

87.010. Division D - Section 3: Qualitative Methodologies Virtual Poster Session.

Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Extending Narrative Inquiry and Autoethnography in Relation to Dewey's Theory of Experience. *Yi (Jenny) Li, University of Ottawa*

Analyzing Data with AI in an Interview-Based Qualitative Study on Multimodality for Polylingual Higher-Education Students. *Olga Gould-Yakovleva, Independent Researcher*
Bringing Qualitative Studies Together: Aims and Impacts of Meta-Synthesis. *Maria Ong, TERC; Nuria Jaumot-Pascual, TERC; Lisette Esmeralda Torres-Gerald, TERC; Christina Silva, TERC*

Evaluating Transformative Effects of Culture and Arts Education Through Traces of "expériences marquantes."
Lihan YU, École normale supérieure de Lyon (ENS Lyon); Jean-Charles Chabanne, École normale supérieure de Lyon (ENS Lyon)

87.010. Division D - Section 4: Multiple and Mixed Methodologies Virtual Poster Session. Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Mapping the Links Between Maternal Overprotection and Preschoolers' Eating Behaviors: A Mixed Methods Network Study. *Ziqin Liu, Macquarie University*
Exploring Black Student Representation in Dual Enrollment: A Critical Race Mixed Methods Study. *Janelle R Clay, Achieve Atlanta*

87.010. Division G - Section 1: Education and Place, Space, Time Virtual Poster Session. Division G - Social Context of Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

The Great India Coaching Train: Impact of Demand for 'Shadow Higher Education System' on Internal Youth Migration in India. *Tanya Ahuja, Indian Institute of Management*
Resolved to thrive: Cultivating critical consciousness through dialogue, agency, and co-constructed community. *Soe Young Lee, Boston University; Xinyu Gu, Boston University; Jessica Wu, Boston University; Thai Daniel, Boston University; Michael Alan Medina, Boston University*
STEM Undergraduate Students and Short-term Study Abroad Program: An Exploratory Study on Intercultural Competence. *Margaret Gatongi, Virginia Commonwealth University; John Fife, Virginia Commonwealth University*
Cultural superiority, Disdain for mainstream norms among Korean immigrant mothers. *Jung - Ah Choi, St. Peter's University*
Not all Movers are the Same: Residential Mobility and School Outcomes in a Large Urban School District. *Chenyang Zhou, Western University; Gus Riveros, Western University*

87.010. Division G - Section 2: Differences and Intersectionalities Virtual Poster Session. Division G - Social Context of Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Exploring the Role of African American English and American Sign Language in Shaping Literacy Development. *Alexis*

Lawton, Clemson University

Unforgetting Belonging: Rethinking Identity, Language, and Adolescent Loneliness in Global Middle Schools. *Lori Nolte, Wilkes University; Jin Joy Mao, Wilkes University*
Black Women Educators' Experiences With Racial and Gendered Microaggressions in K-12. *Valentina Arango-Correa, Rutgers University - New Brunswick*

87.010. Division G - Section 3: Languages, Literacies, and Representations Virtual Poster Session. Division G - Social Context of Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Belonging and Culturally Sustaining Practices in a School Food Program. *Katie Brubacher, University of Alberta; Sarah Harper, University of Alberta*

87.010. Division G - Section 5: Inquiry, Transformation, and Communities Virtual Poster Session. Division G - Social Context of Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Exploring Generative AI in Education: Large Language Models for Topic Modeling and Discourse Analysis. *Wanli Xing, University of Florida; Fan Zhang, University of Florida*
Hiding higher education equity work in plain sight through a practical application of queer theory. *Kristyn Meyer Wood, Harper College*
Practicing Good Relation: Youth, Grief, and the Ethics of Participatory Research. *Tiffany T. Hill, University of Toronto*

87.010. Division G - Section 6: Inquiry in the Social Context of Education Virtual Poster Session. Division G - Social Context of Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Working the Ruins of "Tiger Mom" Parenting: Educational Strategies of Korean Immigrant Mothers. *Jung - Ah Choi, St. Peter's University*
Determinants of Dual Attainment in Academic Achievement and Wellbeing: Evidence from Korea, U.K., and Finland. *Seulki Kim, Korean Educational Development Institute*
Influencer Culture and Chinese University Students' Perceptions of Higher Education. *Jiwen Yang, University of Macau*
(Re)Imagining National Identity: Chinese Students' Everyday Negotiations in a Transnational Context. *Chufan Qiu, Huazhong University of Science and Technology*

87.010. Division H - Section 1: Applied Research in Schools

Virtual Poster Session. Division H - Research, Evaluation and Assessment in Schools; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Youth Inquiry of Traditional Chinese Medicine and Western Medicine Preferences in Local High Schools. *Jianqi Wang, The High School Affiliated to Renmin University of China; Zili Zhang, Pennsylvania State University; Vivian L. Gadsden, University of Pennsylvania*

Who Thrives in the Digital Age? Examining SES, Self-Efficacy, Screen Time, and Digital Literacy. *Hyejeong Lee, University of Texas - San Antonio; Suyoun Kim, Korea University; Tiffany Emanuel, University of Texas - San Antonio*

87.010. Division H - Section 2: Program Evaluation in Schools Virtual Poster Session. Division H - Research, Evaluation and Assessment in Schools; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Virtual or In-Person? Comparative Evaluation of a Pre-health Summer Program for High School Students. *Aihua Wang, Florida State University*

Reimagining ELA for Equity: Evaluating Educative Materials for English Learners Across States. *Zahava Nickell, Empirical Education Inc.; Adam Schellinger, Empirical Education Inc.; Andrew P. Jaciw, Empirical Education Inc.; Aida Walqui, WestEd; Jenna L. Zacamy, Empirical Education Inc.*

87.010. Division H - Section 3: Assessment in Schools Virtual Poster Session. Division H - Research, Evaluation and Assessment in Schools; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Paper-Pencil and Computer Adaptive Test Formats: Comparing Student Psychometrics on a Mathematical Problem-Solving Assessment. *Toni A. May, Binghamton University - SUNY; Gregory E. Stone, University of Toledo; Jonathan D. Bostic, Bowling Green State University; Gabriel Matney, Bowling Green State University; Connor J. Sondergeld, MetriKs; Timothy D. Folger, Binghamton University - SUNY; Yiyun Fan, Binghamton University - SUNY*

Let Me Help You: Near-Peer Teaching in Multimodal Assessments. *Michelle Raquel, The University of Hong Kong; Wim Isidoor Lea Vergult, The University of Hong Kong; Yan LI, The Education University of Hong Kong*

87.010. Division H - Section 4: Accountability in Schools Virtual Poster Session. Division H - Research, Evaluation and Assessment in Schools; Virtual iPresentation Only

Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

From Metrics to Materials: Generative Mechanisms of Formalism in Chinese Educational Inspection. *Hui Zhi, Beijing Normal University*

87.010. Division I - Education in the Professions Virtual Poster Session. Division I - Education in the Professions; Virtual iPresentation Only

Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Exploring Roadblocks to Success: Minoritized Medical Students' Experiences of Educational Technologies. *Racheal Lee, Uniformed Services University of the Health Sciences; Steven J. Durning, Uniformed Services University of the Health Sciences; Marina Shapiro, Uniformed Services University of the Health Sciences; Anita Samuel, Uniformed Services University of the Health Sciences*

The Development of an Instrument to Measure Engineering Identity. *Yifan Wang, Fordham University; Yi Ding, Fordham University; Qian Wang, Manhattan College; Alesia Mickle Moldavan, Georgia Southern University*
Undergraduate Engineering Students' Motivation, Self-Efficacy, and Student Adjustment in Relation to Engineering Identity and Academic Achievement. *Yifan Wang, Fordham University; Yi Ding, Fordham University; Qian Wang, Manhattan College; Alesia Mickle Moldavan, Georgia Southern University*

Reliability of Article-Based Testing: Insights from the Omega Coefficient Family. *Qiao Lin, American Board of Psychiatry & Neurology; David Shin, American Board of Psychiatry and Neurology, Inc.; Jeffrey M. Lyness, American Board of Psychiatry and Neurology, Inc.; Huaping Sun, The American Board of Anesthesiology*

87.010. Division J - Section 2a: College Student Access, Trajectories, and Transitions Virtual Poster Session. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Virtual iPresentation Only

Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

First, Do No Harm. But Can We Do Better? An Evaluation of a Corequisite Reform. *Zeyu Xu, American Institutes for Research; Ben Backes, American Institutes for Research*
Postsecondary Access and Completion: A Meta-Analysis of Dual Enrollment and Early College High School Participation. *Justin C. Ortagus, University of Florida; Xiaodan Hu, Southern Methodist University; Hope Allechin, University of Florida; Rachel Dean Divaker, University of Florida; Terri D. Pigott, Georgia State University*
Building Stackable Education and Career Credentials into

Healthcare with Low-Income Students. *Catherine R. Cooper, University of California - Santa Cruz; Lucia Vitale, University of California - Santa Cruz; Jordan Sitea, University of California - Santa Cruz; Cristine H. Chopra, Santa Cruz County Office of Education; Maria Rocha-Ruiz, University of California - Santa Cruz*

87.010. Division J - Section 2c: Assessing College Student Success and Impact Virtual Poster Session. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Predictors of College Degree Completion among Students with Foster Care Experience in California. *Nathanael J. Okpych, University of Connecticut; Jennifer Geiger, University of Illinois at Chicago*
Integrating Canvas Engagement Data and Student Evaluations of Teaching to Predict Academic Performance. *Qingmin Shi, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Shiloh Fling, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Tina Nelson, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*

87.010. Division J - Section 3: Organization, Management, and Leadership Virtual Poster Session. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Crossing the Chasm: Interpretation as the Bridge Between Assessment and Action in Organizational Learning Processes. *Emily Braught, Indiana University*
A Framework for University Contributions to Climate Change: Pathways, Priorities, and Action Models. *Yujie LI, Shanghai Jiao Tong University*
Triangulating Excellence: The Dynamic Interplay Between Regulators, Teaching Centers, and National Forums in Higher Education. *Nizar Bitar, The Max Stern Yezreel Valley College; Nitza Davidovich, Ariel University*

87.010. Division J - Section 4: Faculty, Curriculum, and Teaching Virtual Poster Session. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Integrating AI in Higher Education: Faculty Insights on Syllabus Policies and Student Use. *Mahmoud Altalouli, State University of New York Brockport; Amy L. Shema, College at Brockport - SUNY; Jialin Yan, University of Rochester*
Retaining Faculty in Higher Education: Examining the Crucial Role of Sense of Belonging. *Jennifer Reid, Virginia Commonwealth University; Maiké I. Philipsen, Virginia Commonwealth University; Julie Charbonnier, Virginia*

Commonwealth University; Pat Githens, Virginia Commonwealth University; Adelaide Alexander, Virginia Commonwealth University; Mary A. Hermann, Loyola University - New Orleans; Susan Kornstein, Virginia Commonwealth University

Beyond the Loop: Broadening How We Think About Assessment Use. *Emily Braught, Indiana University*
Classroom Assessment Validity in Dynamic Postsecondary Systems. *Maxine Britto, Brock University; Tiffany L. Gallagher, Brock University*

Toward Transformative UDL Practice: A Community-Based Assessment of Institutional Understanding, Usage, and Cultural Barriers. *Molly McKeon, University of Colorado - Denver*

Learning Together: Student Voices and Experiences in Co-Created Educational Design. *Nataliya Pakhotina, Texas A&M University; Rayyan Zulfiqar, Texas A&M University; Mahjabin Chowdhury, Texas A&M University*

Rethinking the Supplemental Instruction Model to Meet the Needs of Community College Students. *Catherine Mas, n/a; Stephanie J. Jones, Texas Tech University*

Investigating Classroom Patterns and Behaviors Based on Classroom Observation Protocol for Undergraduate STEM (COPUS). *Yousif Muten, Auburn University*

87.010. Division J - Section 6: Society, Culture, History, and Change Virtual Poster Session. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Perpetuating the Devaluation of Historically Feminized Academic Fields: Use of Public Funds in a Formula Funding Approach. *Valerie Paton, Texas Tech University; Catherine Shepard, Texas Tech University; Stephanie J. Jones, Texas Tech University*

Fat-Bodied Learners And College Websites: Will I fit in? *Sara Lucas, Northern Illinois University*

A Study of Chinese College Students' Identification with Traditional Chinese Culture Research Objective. *Hong Zhang, Qufu Normal University; Hanyu Xing, Qufu Normal University, China*

Advancing Reconciliation in Higher Education: Insights from Student Affairs Professionals. *Danielle Gardiner Milln, University of Alberta*

87.010. Division K - Section 01: Teaching and Teacher Education in the Content Areas Virtual Poster Session. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Beyond Teaching: How English Teachers Shape Aspirations. *Yi*

Feng, Durham University

Constructing Futures: How Emerging Educators See Math and Literacy Working Together. *Catherine Susin, Brock University; Tiffany L. Gallagher, Brock University*

87.010. Division K - Section 02: Teacher Agency, Activism, and Leadership Virtual Poster Session. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

How do Social Networks of STEM Teachers Change after Participating in a Conference? Are These Changes Sustainable Months After? *Adem Ekmekci, Rice University; Bryan Rebar, University of Oregon; Stephanie Salomone, University of Portland; Jenna Porter, California State University - Sacramento; Donna L. Ross, San Diego State University; Jenefer E. Husman, University of Oregon*

Teaching from the Land: Indigenous Educators and the Transformation of Teacher Leadership. *John Kambutu, University of Wyoming; Lydiah Nganga, University of Wyoming*

From Streets to Classrooms: Forging and Enacting Teacher Agency in South Korea. *Hyeokeun Kwon, Yonsei University; Won Pyo Hong, Yonsei University; Eunjin Jeong, Yonsei University*

The Commitment to Ethical Teaching Leadership in the Selection of Future Teachers. *María José Latorre-Medina, FACULTY OF EDUCATION, ECONOMY, AND TECHNOLOGY OF CEUTA, UNIVERSITY OF GRANADA; Purificación Pérez-García, University of Granada*

87.010. Division K - Section 03: Teachers' Lives, Identities, and Journeys Virtual Poster Session. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

How Social Support Cultivates Teacher Digital Resilience? A Serial Mediation Analysis Based on Social Cognitive Theory. *Mingyu Wang, Hangzhou Normal University; Jing Wang, Hangzhou Normal University; Wenjing Zeng, Hangzhou Normal University*

Becoming Teachers at the Margins: Local Teacher Identity in Chinese Internationalized Schools(CIS). *XIAOLU BAI, University College London - IOE*

Social Justice Teacher Preparation: Throughlines Across University, Teacher Residency, and First Year in the Classroom. *Cori Salmerón, Georgia State University*

Challenges and Social Stigma of Male Gay and Transgender Foreign Teachers: A Qualitative Study. *Luis Miguel Dos Santos, Hong Kong Shue Yan University, Hong Kong; Litong Qi, Hong Kong Shue Yan University; Hongyan Wang, Binghamton University - SUNY; Ying Li, Binghamton*

University - SUNY

Teacher Vitality and its Generative Mechanism: A Key Issue in Building a High-quality Education System in China. *Nan Hao, Zhengzhou University; Tianqi Cao, Zhengzhou University*

87.010. Division K - Section 04: Foundations of Teaching and Teacher Education for Socio-Cultural, Racial, and Intersecting Minoritized Identities Virtual Poster Session. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education;

Virtual iPresentation Only

Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Feminist Pedagogy in Instructional Design: A Content Analysis of the Journal of Applied Instructional Design. *Melissa Baysingar, Harper College*

Resisting Erasure: Racialized Teacher Candidates Rewriting the Future of Teacher Education. *Wenefe Capili-Balbalin, University of Ottawa*

Unforgetting to Imagine: Pre-service Teachers Use Photovoice to Envision Equitable Education. *Perla Barbosa, Salem State University; Priscila Leal, University of Hawaii - Manoa*

Enabling Transgressions: A Content Analysis of Racial Literacy Development Through Pre-Service Teachers' Reflective Journals. *Salandra Grice-Johnson, Sam Houston State University; Alexis M. Terry, American University*

Fostering Social-Emotional Learning in Teacher Education: Experiences from a Novel culturally adapted SEL Course. *Eman Abu-Hanna Nahhas, Oranim Academic College of Education and Gordon College; Hanadi Abu Ahmad, Beit Berl College-Israel*

87.010. Division K - Section 05: Pre-Service Teacher Coursework and Clinical Practice Virtual Poster Session.

Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Virtual iPresentation Only

Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Ethical Formation in the Practicum: Mentoring Pre-service Teachers in the Face of Contemporary Educational Challenges. *Laia Lluç Molins, Universitat Oberta de Catalunya; Eduard Masdeu-Yélamos, Universitat Oberta de Catalunya*

Understanding Secondary ELA Pre-Service Teachers' Curricular Experiences: Insights from Clinical Placements in Diverse School Contexts. *Jessie O'Brien-Sheats, Lehigh University; Brook Sawyer, Lehigh University*

A Pilot Study of Phase-Specific Feedback Loops and Interventions in an Elementary Teacher Program. *Brittany M. Adams, University of Alabama; Cortney Dilgard, University of Alabama; Amanda Cramer, University of*

Alabama; Jennifer Pate, University of Alabama

Profiling Pre-service Teachers in Blended Learning: A Dual-Dimensional Framework Integrating Behavioral Engagement and Dispositional Readiness. *jing wang, 华东师范大学*

Beyond the Fertile Paradox: Preservice Teachers' Steps Past Awareness to Action Against Injustice. *Eleni Duret, San Jose State University; Gena Merliss, Nazareth University*
Collaborative Lesson Design Between Pre-Service Mathematics Teachers and AI: A Mixed-Method Study. *rui zhao, east china normal university*

Expansive Framing as a Pathway for Fostering Transfer of Teacher Learning to Diverse Contexts. *Tripp Harris, University of South Carolina*

87.010. Division K - Section 06: In-Service Teacher Professional Development Virtual Poster Session.
Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Empowering Teachers: An Empirical Study on the Digital competency of Early Childhood Teachers in China. *Shiduo Wang, East China Normal University; Yutong Li, University College London - IOE*

Bridging the Gap Between Teacher Professional Development and Classroom Practice: An Equity-Driven, Collaborative Approach. *Salima Dhanani, Florida International University*

Exploring Factors Influencing Play-Based Learning in Supporting Elementary School Students' Social-Emotional Development from the Perspectives of Teachers. *Vy Van Dao, University of Social Sciences and Humanities-Vietnam National University HCM*

Sustainability in Professional Learning Communities: Historical Insights and Future Strategies. *Chinyere I Odia, University of North Texas; Sukai Durosimi, East Fort Worth Montessori Academy*

Investigating K-12 Teachers' Perception of Incorporating Generative AI into Students' Tasks. *Gyeongri Kim, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Peter Samuelson Wardrip, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Mapping the Journey to Exceptional Schooling for Multilingual Learners. *Naomi Flynn, University of Reading; Annela Teemant, Indiana University - Indianapolis*

Context-Sensitive AI Chatbots for Scalable Teacher Professional Development: A Mixed-Methods Evaluation in Austrian Higher Education. *Thomas Leitgeb, University of Education Burgenland; Michael Leitgeb, University College Of Teacher Education Burgenland*

Examining Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) Among In-Service Secondary Teachers in Taiwan: Evidence From a Pilot Survey Study. *Chin-Yi Huang, Indiana University of Pennsylvania; Julie Winneur Ankrum, Indiana University of Pennsylvania*

87.010. Division K - Section 07: Teacher Educator Initial and Ongoing Development Virtual Poster Session. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Dismantling the Ivory Tower: The Positioning of "The University" on a Student Teaching Triad. *Diana Murtaugh, Binghamton University - SUNY*

When Technology Meets Emotion: A Study on University Teachers' Caring Behaviors in Online Teaching. *诗如王, 华中科技大学; 帅龙李, Central China Normal University*

GenAI in STEM Teacher Education: Investigating the Tensions and Emerging Possibilities of Adoption and Use. *Yvonne Franco, University of Tampa; Ruthmae Sears, University of South Florida; Stephanie A. Arthur, University of South Florida; Sandra Vernon-Jackson, University of South Florida*

87.010. Division K - Section 08: Teacher Recruitment, Induction, and Mentoring Virtual Poster Session.
Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Reimagining Mentorship in Language Teacher Education: A Relation-Centered Transpositional Framework and a TEAM Practice Model. *Huili Hong, Vanderbilt University; Li Wei, UCL Institute of Education*

87.010. Division K - Section 09: Innovative Design and Models for Teaching and Teacher Education Virtual Poster Session. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

From Amnesia to Agency: Reclaiming History for Justice-Oriented Educational Futures. *Tara Ratnam, Independent Researcher*

Instructional Agency in the Digital Era: Mapping Teacher Beliefs, Development, and Technology Use. *Suyoun Kim, Korea University; Hyejeong Lee, University of Texas - San Antonio*

Drifting in the Library: Leading Students to Unexpected Texts Through a Situation. *Christina Jones, Education Library; Micaela Deogracias, Indiana University; Gustave J. Weltsek, Indiana University*

Empowering Educators: Teachers' Perspectives on Generative

AI in Multimodal Digital Design Education. *Youwen Shi, The Chinese University of Hong Kong*

Centering Cultural Wealth: A Case Study of Refugee Girls' Education at Global Village Project. *Sarah S. Williams, University of North Georgia; Genevieve Gooley, Western Governors University*

How Secondary English Teachers Integrate AI-Guided Chatbots in Writing Feedback: Insights from Activity Theory. *Yuan Yao, Hong Kong Polytechnic University; Xinhua Zhu, Hong Kong Polytechnic University; Longhai Xiao, Zhejiang University; Hongbiao Yin, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Qi Lu, The Chinese University of Hong Kong*

Innovative and Intentional by Design: A Global Teacher Education Model Honoring Histories and Cultivating Futures. *Fatima Hasan Bailey, Sharjah Education Academy*

Future-Oriented Reflection in Simulation-Based Learning: A Freirean Lens on Teacher Development Across Modalities. *Orna Levin, Achva Academic College; Heidi Flavian, Achva Academic College*

87.010. Division L - Section 1: Governance, Politics, and Legal Issues Virtual Poster Session. Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Historic Parallels and Future Risks: Explaining Ohio's Governance Shift with Punctuated Equilibrium Theory. *Helen Buck-Pavlick, The Ohio State University; Ann M. Allen, The Ohio State University*

87.010. Division L - Section 4: Social, Political, and Cultural Contexts Virtual Poster Session. Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Research Culture in Georgian University and Its Role in the Development of Doctoral Education. *Tatia Kalandadze, ilia state university*

Bullying Constructs and Manifestations: A Comparative Study of Japan and the US. *Yurika Doi, Grinnell College*

A Human Rights-Based Framework for Trauma-Informed Pedagogy: Advancing Educational Access and Equity. *Stephani Nummelin, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Rohan Tapiawala, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*

87.010. Division L - Section 6: Social Policy, Inequality, and Student Outcomes Virtual Poster Session. Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Education, Inequality and Teenage Pregnancy in England: Policy Lessons for Equitable Support. *Yingxiang Chen, University of Bath; Liang Yuitan, Shenzhen Senior High School (Group) North Campus*

Why are Rural Students Absent from School? Evidence from West Virginia. *Michael A. Gottfried, University of Pennsylvania; Erin Gill, University of Pennsylvania; Stephen Colby Woods, University of Pennsylvania*

Reimagining Civic Literacy: A Comparative Study of Hong Kong's Liberal Studies Reform and U.S. Social Studies Standards. *Yunlu Wang, Georgia State University*

87.010. Division L - Section 7: Policy Implementation, Analysis, and Impact Virtual Poster Session. Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Improving Literacy Instruction at Scale: State Reading Policy Implementation and Capacity Building in Small and Rural Schools. *Sarah J Zuckerman, University of Nebraska - Lincoln; Michael Hebert, University of California - Irvine; Pamela Bazis, University of Nebraska - Lincoln; Sara Wing, University of Nebraska - Lincoln; Janet Bohaty, University of Nebraska - Lincoln; Nathan Speer, University of Nebraska - Lincoln; Rachel E. Schachter, University of Illinois at Chicago; Marc Goodrich, Texas A&M University; Derek Rodgers, University of Iowa*

"What Works, for Whom, and Under What Conditions" in Implementing Improvement Science at Scale. *Ariel Tichnor-Wagner, Boston University; Elizabeth Barcay, Boston University; Rohan Arcot, Boston University; Leslie Camilo Sears, Boston University*

Belonging without a Place: A Critical Policy Analysis of First-Gen Dual Enrollment Supports. *Shelby Terral, University of Houston*

Educational Leaders Navigating AI: Policy Challenges and Opportunities in K-12 Implementation. *Juhee Kim, University of Idaho; Elizabeth Wargo, University of Idaho*

Investigate Differences in Policy Enactment between Chinese and England Higher Education Reforms. *Dandan Li, University of Bath*

Implementing Digital Curriculum Reform: Policy, Governance, and Equity in Large-Scale Educational Transformation. *Christina Chinas, Durham University*

2030 Is Almost Here: A Holistic Approach of Measuring and Exploring the Progress of SDG4. *Zehorit Dadon Golan, Rutgers University; Wendy M. Purcell, Rutgers University*

Reassessing Graduate Program Evaluation in Brazil: A Critical Perspective on the CAPES System through the Sociology of Education. *Vanessa Cotta Silveira Machado, Universidade Federal de Ouro Preto; Jose Rubens Lima Jardimino, Federal University of Ouro Preto*

The Effects of the No Child Left Behind Act on Native American Languages: A Case Study on Navajo Public Schools in Arizona. *Jiaheng Yu, Northern Arizona University*

87.010. International Relations Committee Virtual Poster Session. International Relations Committee; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Preservice Teacher Development through Transnational Reflective Practices: A Bildung- Oriented Approach. *Doris A. Kroiss, University of North Carolina - Greensboro; Wiebke J. Langer, University of Hamburg; Ye He, University of North Carolina - Greensboro*

87.010. SIG-Accreditation, Assessment, and Program Evaluation in Education Preparation Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Accreditation, Assessment, and Program Evaluation in Education Preparation; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

A Pilot Study Exploring Education Majors' Reasoning About P-12 Classroom Disparities. *Amber Janel Adgeron, University of North Dakota; Emma Pitt, Northeastern University; Rebecca Peretz-Lange, Vassar College; John D. Coley, Northeastern University*

87.010. SIG-Action Research Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Action Research; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Exploring Pedagogical Practices in STEM Higher Education: An Action Research Study. *Menaka Abraham, University of Washington - Tacoma; Meredith Wronowski, University of Dayton*

87.010. SIG-Adolescence and Youth Development Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Adolescence and Youth Development; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Classroom Dynamics and Deviant Behavior Among Junior High School Students: A Multi-level Analysis. *Siwei Xu; Tianzhe Chen, University of Cambridge; Jiarui Luo, The Hong Kong Polytechnic University; Tongmao Li, The University of Florida*
Comfort, Care, and Connection: A Qualitative Inquiry into

Young Adolescents' Perspectives on Belonging in School. *Tonje Mari Molyneux, University of British Columbia; Anusha Kassin, University of British Columbia; Jenna D. Shapka, University of British Columbia; Eva Oberle, University of British Columbia*

The Sexual Health Awareness Scale: Development, Validation, and Initial Applications. *Ozlem Sener, Bartin University; Suleyman Kahraman, Beykent University*

87.010. SIG-Advanced Technologies for Learning Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Advanced Technologies for Learning; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

AI-Supported Emotional Well-Being in Learning: A Review of Empirical Studies. *Run Wen, Xi'an Jiaotong-Liverpool University; Na Li, Xi'an Jiaotong-Liverpool University; Manolis Mavrikis, University College London*

87.010. SIG-Arts and Inquiry in the Visual and Performing Arts in Education Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Arts and Inquiry in the Visual and Performing Arts in Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Unforgotten Practices, Future Possibilities: Puppetry, Pedagogy and the Integrated Arts. *Laura McEntee, Mary Immaculate College; Edmond Gubbins, Mary Immaculate College*

87.010. SIG-Arts and Learning Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Arts and Learning; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Digital Leadership and ICT Competence Among Music Educators: Evidence from Chinese Universities. *Xingzhi Guan, UCSI University; Jing Cai, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia*
From Shared Histories to Divergent Futures: A Comparative Analysis of Music Curriculum Policy in China and South Korea. *ZITONG LI, Ulsan of university*

87.010. SIG-Arts-Based Educational Research Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Arts-Based Educational Research; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Collaging Co-Mentorship: A Feminist Approach for Mentorship, Troubling Norms, and Imagining Otherwise. *Lucy E. Bailey, Oklahoma State University; Stacie L.*

Warner, Oklahoma State University; Lindsey Abernathy, Oklahoma State University

Art-Based Research, Decoloniality, and Gender-Based Violence: Voices of Women Students from India. *Ruchi Saini, University of Central Florida*
Bridging Silos Through Dance Pedagogy: Integrating Biology, Geography, and Embodied Teaching in Graduate Education. *lilin chen, Beijing Normal University*

87.010. SIG-Asian Americans and Pacific Islanders in Education and Research Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Asian Americans and Pacific Islanders in Education and Research; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Examination of the Pygmalion Effect of the Filial Piety on Asian American Students. *Sham`ah Md-Yunus, Eastern Illinois University; Joohi Lee, University of Texas - Arlington*
Bridging Worlds Through Literacy: A Culturally Sustaining Book Club for Korean Immigrant Parents and Korean American Children. *Jiyeong Joann Yi, Iowa State University; Constance C. Beecher, Iowa State University; Kunhui Kim, Iowa State University*

87.010. SIG-Bilingual Education Research Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Bilingual Education Research; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Co-Designing Justice-Oriented ESL Curricula: A Humanizing Approach to Research-Practice Partnerships. *Marisol Masso, Michigan State University*
ARCS-iLearn : An AI Agent-Based Vocabulary Learning Framework Grounded in ARCS Motivation Theory. *Yuxi Zhang, central china normal university; jianping huang, Beijing Normal University*

87.010. SIG-Biographical and Documentary Research Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Biographical and Documentary Research; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Education as Liberation : Biography and Freedom in the Lives of Krishnamurti, Tagore and Gandhi. *Raji Swaminathan, University of Wisconsin - Milwaukee*
Life Writing, Embodiment, and Becoming: The Body as Pedagogy. *Amanda Kingston, Syracuse University; Stacie L. Warner, Oklahoma State University; Lindsey Abernathy, Oklahoma State University; Lucy E. Bailey, Oklahoma State University*

From Forgotten to Remembered: Using Oral Histories to Reclaim Rural BIPOC Educational Experiences through a Black Feminist-Womanist Lens. *Alexis Grant-Panting, Texas Woman's University*

Four Poetic Inquirers in Ancient China: Lu Ji, Liu Xie, Zhong Rong, and Tao Yuanming. *Botao Wu, University of British Columbia*

Auto/biographical Strategies of Women's Basketball Coaches as Educators. *Thalia Mulvihill, Ball State University*

87.010. SIG-Bourdieu in Educational Research Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Bourdieu in Educational Research; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

'By Chance' or 'by Choice'? A Bourdieusian Study of Graduates from Elite Universities as Schoolteachers. *Ruoxin Wang, University of South Australia; Guanglun Michael Mu, University of South Australia*

87.010. SIG-Brain, Neurosciences and Education Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Brain, Neurosciences and Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Emotional Neural Choreography: Parent-Child Brain Synchrony During Valenced Interactions. *Yihui Wang, Shanghai Normal University; Yihan Zhang, University of Macau; Lidian Huang, University of Macau; Juan Zhang, University of Macau*
Gaze, Language, and Attention: Demonstrative Use and Joint Attention in High Functioning Autism Spectrum. *Alaz Aydin, Middle East Technical University; Murat Perit Cakir, Middle East Technical University*

87.010. SIG-Career & Technical Education and Workplace Learning Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Career & Technical Education and Workplace Learning; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Collaborative Problem-Solving and Online Self-Efficacy in Technical and Vocational Higher Education: A Regression Tree Analysis. *Gonzalo Salas, Universidad de Chile; Daniela Edith Luengo-Aravena, Spencer Foundation*
Reimagining Teacher Leadership: Bridging Leadership Gaps with Competency-Based Digital Apprenticeships. *Matthew Bornak, Pennsylvania State University*

87.010. SIG-Caribbean and African Studies in Education

Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Caribbean and African Studies in Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

A Socio-Cultural Reconceptualization of African History Through Literature and Historiography. *Oladipupo Adedamola Ogunfeibo, University of British Columbia*

Learning Management Systems in Under-Resourced Settings: Insights from Nigerian Private Primary and Secondary Schools. *Ijeoma Aboaja, Ottawa University*

87.010. SIG-Cognition and Assessment Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Cognition and Assessment; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Understanding How Students Learn from Multiple Sources: A Latent Variable Approach to Assessing Comprehension. *Zhaocheng Wu, Mississippi State University; Andrew Potter, Arizona State University; Danielle S. McNamara, Arizona State University*

Psychometrics Oversights: A Systematic Literature Review of Reliability, Validation and Fairness in Reading Self-Concept Measurements. *Onur Ramazan, University of Hong Kong; Robert W. Danielson, Washington State University - Spokane; Shenghai Dai, Washington State University; Chad M. Gotch, Washington State University*

87.010. SIG-Computer and Internet Application in Education Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Computer and Internet Application in Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Design Mode from the Start: Co-constructed futures through distributed epistemic agency. *Robert Huang, University of Toronto*

Enhance College Students' Argumentation Skills and Critical Thinking through ChatGPT-assisted In-class Debates. *Jiateng Zhou, Beijing Normal University; Yifei Diao, Central China Normal University; Jiawen Gou, Beijing Normal University; Ziyi Li, University of Cambridge; Wei Gao, Central China Normal University*

Pre-service Teachers' Knowledge Construction from Supported Online Inquiry: Evidence from Tagclouds. *Ying Xie, Northern Illinois University; Shu-yuan Lin, Idaho State University*

87.010. SIG-Critical Educators for Social Justice Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Critical Educators for Social Justice; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Seeds of Resistance: From Linguistic Wounds to Pedagogical Advocacy. *Leticia de la Garza, University of Central Arkansas*

Chalk, Codes, and Community: Reimagining Public Spaces for Equity and Multilingual Belonging. *Robert Niewiadomski, Fordham University*

87.010. SIG-Critical Examination of Race, Ethnicity, Class and Gender in Education Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Critical Examination of Race, Ethnicity, Class and Gender in Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Navigating Belonging: Minoritized Educators' Experiences of Inclusiveness in Schools. *Dilek Kayaalp, University of North Florida; Madalina F. Tanase, University of North Florida*

Invisible Structures, Visible Struggles: Intersectional Barriers Faced by Black Female Students with Disabilities. *ruiwen song, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia*

Can Racial Bias in Teachers' Decisions Be Reduced? Evidence from a Survey Experiment in French Middle Schools. *Charlotte CORCHETE, Sciences Po Paris*

Deconstructing and Reframing 'Azad Khayal Aurat': Women's Identity in Indian Higher Education. *Esra Nizami, University of Massachusetts - Amherst*

Positive Black Racial Identity and Post-Secondary Success among Black males. *Beverly-Jean Daniel, Toronto Metropolitan University; Alana C. Butler, Queen's University - Kingston*

87.010. SIG-Critical Peace Education Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Critical Peace Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Pedagogies of Refusal: How Gazan Educators Resist the Collapse of Higher Education During War. *Stephanie Robinson, University of North Texas*

87.010. SIG-Critical Posthuman and Postfoundational Studies in Education Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Critical Posthuman and Postfoundational Studies in Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

The Rhizomatic Learning Paths in Becoming Post Qualitative Inquiry Researcher. *Aida Kairienė, Klaipėda university*

From "千人一声" to Posthuman Polyphony: Unforgetting Histories, Assembling Futures in Chinese Music Education. *Yaxin Li, University of Cambridge*

87.010. SIG-Decolonial, Postcolonial, and Anti-Colonial Studies in Education Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Decolonial, Postcolonial, and Anti-Colonial Studies in Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Youth, Museums, and Ownership of the Past—Reimagining Education Through the Java Man and Repatriation. *Joel E. Berends, Michigan State University*

87.010. SIG-Democratic Citizenship in Education Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Democratic Citizenship in Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Universities as Civic Ecologies: A Quantitative Study of Institutional Logics and Civic Engagement Predictors. *Ainslee Jacgdish Preciado, University of California - Los Angeles*

87.010. SIG-Design and Technology Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Design and Technology; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Enhancing Instructor Self-Efficacy Through AI Training in Higher Education. *Amani Itani, University of Houston; Dina Shouman, Lebanese International University*

Gamified Storytelling App for Medical English: A Mixed-Methods Design and Impact Evaluation. *Zahra Zolfaghari, Shiraz University - Iran; Shiraz University of Medical Sciences; Zahra karimian, Shiraz Ununiversity of Medical Sciences; nahid Zarifsaniey., Shiraz Ununiversity of medical sciences; amiryosuf farahmandi, Shiraz Ununiversity of medical sciences*

87.010. SIG-Disability Studies in Education Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Disability Studies in Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Centering Disabled Students' Evaluation of Universal Design for Learning Pedagogy: An Innovative Teaching Project. *Molly McKeon, University of Colorado - Denver*

87.010. SIG-Early Education and Child Development Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Early Education and Child Development; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to

3:00pm

Participants:

Gender-Specific Parental Influences on Neural Pathways of Children's Emotion Regulation. *Lidian Huang, University of Macau; Yihui Wang, Shanghai Normal University; Yihan Zhang, University of Macau; Juan Zhang, University of Macau*

Exploring the Role of Spanish Classroom Characteristics for Head Start Children's Academic Outcomes. *Ashley Diane Boros, The Ohio State University; Ji Young Choi, The Ohio State University*

Gentrification and Universal Pre-K: Examining Equity and Access in a South Boston Childcare Center. *Da Hei Ku, University of Massachusetts - Boston*

The Differential Impact of Pre-K on Homeless, Low-Income, and Non-Disadvantaged Children. *Travis S. Wright, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Scoping Review: Early Math Acquisition in Myanmar vs. China and the U.S. *Khin Aye Chan Thein, The Education University of Hong Kong; Yi Shen, The Education University of Hong Kong; Hui Li, The Education University of Hong Kong*

87.010. SIG-Educational Change Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Educational Change; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

A Professional Development to Support Upper-Elementary Teachers' Self-Efficacy to Implement Number Talks. *Kiera Kullaga, Monmouth University; Vecihi Serbay Zambak, Monmouth University*

Understanding COVID-19 Learning Loss: A Global Scoping Review of Standardized Test Outcomes for Grades 1–12. *Naichen Zhao, University of Denver*

87.010. SIG-Environmental Education Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Environmental Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

When Nature Didn't Cooperate: Children's Perspectives on a Failed Conservation Project. *Adiv Gal, Kibbutzim College*
Unheard Climate Voices: Indigenous Bedouin Youth at the Crossroads of Place, Climate Change, and Justice. *Shaima Alokbe, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev; Orit Ben-Zvi Assaraf, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev*

Between Hope and Despair: Holistic and Interdisciplinary Climate Change Education for Teacher Trainees. *Netta Baryosef-Paz, Kibbutzim College; Dafna Gan, The Open University of Israel*

The Unexplored Relationships Between Forest Schools and Climate Change: The Parental Perspective. *Moriya Netzer, University of Haifa; Dafna Gan, The Open University of*

Israel; Ofira Ayalon, University of Haifa

From Intention to Impact: Pre-Service Visions of Student Agency in Climate and Sustainability Education. *Dilraba Anayatova, Arizona State University; Andrea E. Weinberg, Arizona State University; Michelle Jordan, Arizona State University; Nicole Oster, Arizona State University*

The Role of Urban Intentional Community in Advancing Environmental Sustainability Education. *Shoshan Barkan-Eran, Hakibbutzim College of Education; Dafna Gan, The Open University of Israel*

Examining Ontario's Pre- and In-service Elementary Teachers' Knowledge about Climate Change and Climate Change Education. *Shiva Javanmardi, Western University; Anton Puvirajah, Western University*

Non-Formal Educators' Use of Artificial Intelligence in Environmental Education. *Yue Li, University of Florida; Megan Ennes, University of Florida; Jaehyun Ahn, University of Florida*

87.010. SIG-Experiential Education and Community Engagement: Scholarship and Practice Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Experiential Education and Community Engagement: Scholarship and Practice; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Teaching with Place: Developing Preservice Teacher Identity Through Outdoor Learning and Reflection. *Verdah Rehan, Clemson University; Steph N. Dean, George Mason University*

87.010. SIG-Faculty Teaching, Evaluation, and Development Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Faculty Teaching, Evaluation, and Development; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Reigniting Mid-Career Scholarship: A Faculty-Led Writing Boot Camp Grounded in Self-Determination Theory. *Jackie HeeYoung Kim, Georgia Southern University; Tracy Linderholm, University of North Carolina - Wilmington; E. Anthony Muhammad, Georgia Southern University; Antonio P. Gutierrez de Blume, Georgia Southern University*

Bridging the Skills Gap: Reimagining Faculty Development Through Centers for Teaching and Learning. *Nizar Bitar, The Max Stern Yezreel Valley College; Nitza Davidovich, Ariel University*

87.010. SIG-Family, School, Community Partnerships Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Family, School, Community Partnerships; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Partnerships among Families, Schools, and Communities for Multilingual Learners: Educator Aspirations and Promising Practices. *Ye He, University of North Carolina - Greensboro; Donather Daudi Magabe, University of North Carolina - Greensboro; Sipehele Qwabe, University of North Carolina - Greensboro; Tiffany Lee Smith Tovey, University of North Carolina - Greensboro; Bryan C. Hutchins, University of North Carolina - Greensboro*
Determinants of Governance Quality in Elementary and Secondary Education: Evidence from Seoul, South Korea. *Junghun Hwang, Seoul National University; Moonyoung Eom, Seoul National University*

87.010. SIG-Holistic Education Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Holistic Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Wisdom Illumination Education System (Secularized Pedagogy of the Five Illuminating Wisdoms): Framework for New Education. *yang ye, wuming culture media Ltd*

87.010. SIG-Indigenous Peoples of the Americas Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Indigenous Peoples of the Americas; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Towards Otherwise in Indigenous Education: Anishinaabe Beadwork Meets the Decolonial Imaginary. *Melissa Twance, Lakehead University*
Journeys Through STEM: Nurturing Indigenous Pathways of Persistence. *Nuria Jaumot-Pascual, TERC; Jessica M. Karch, TERC; Maria Ong, TERC; Jameson David Lopez, University of Arizona; Tiffany D. Smith, AISES*

87.010. SIG-Informal Learning Environment Research Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Informal Learning Environment Research; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Unlocking learner creativity through a robotics-enhanced story creation summer camp: A pilot study. *Qijie Vicky Cai, Towson University; Pei Ge, Towson University*

87.010. SIG-Instructional Technology Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Instructional Technology; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

A Tale of Four Teachers: Integrating Desmos in High School

Geometry After Professional Development. *Matthew Vazzana, Freehold Township High School; Vecihi Serbay Zambak, Monmouth University*

Empirical Study of Stages of Concern and Influencing Factors in Chinese Rural Music Teachers' Multimedia Integration. *Xuejing Zhang, Universiti Sains Malaysia; Wan Ahmad Jaafar Wan Yahaya, Universiti Sains Malaysia*

Leveraging Learning Analytics to Foster Self-Regulated Learning: A Multi-Semester Design-Based Research Study. *Kun Huang, University of Kentucky; Anita Lee-Post, University of Kentucky; Michael Stacy, University of Kentucky; Ryan Flores, University of Kentucky*

When and How Students Engage with Augmented Generative AI During Mathematical Modeling Tasks. *Eunhye Flavin, Georgia Institute of Technology; Cristian Castaneda, Georgia State University*

87.010. SIG-International Studies Virtual Poster Session. SIG-International Studies; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Examining the Association Between Intercultural Dispositions and Global Competence Across Various Cultural Contexts. *Jinpeng Niu, Southwest University*

Teachers' Training and Competence for Digital Mediation in Special Schools in Spain. *Esther Chiner, University of Alicante; Marcos Gómez-Puerta, University of Alicante; Cristina Miralles-Cardona, Universidad de Alicante; Maria Cristina Cardona, University of Alicante*

Leveraging Online Research Experience for International University Admission: A Chinese Student Perspective. *Junjian Gao, Wenzhou-Kean University; Yolanda Sealey-Ruiz, Teachers College, Columbia University; Jinyi Ren, Wenzhou-Kean University*

The Multifaceted Ethical Dilemmas of Postdoctoral Researchers: Toward Equitable Policies in International Mobility. *Yosef Katanov, Bar-Ilan University; Orly Shapira, Tel Aviv University; Annette Bamberger, Bar-Ilan University*

87.010. SIG-Language and Social Processes Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Language and Social Processes; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Preservice Clinicians' Language Ideologies, Translanguaging Stance and Confidence to Work with Emergent Bilinguals. *Grace Lee, University of Houston; Monique Mills, University of Houston*

87.010. SIG-Latina/o/x Research Issues Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Latina/o/x Research Issues; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to

3:00pm

Participants:

Social Media As A Supplemental Tool for Harm Reduction Education Among Queer Latine. *Benjamin Coronado, University of California - Santa Cruz; Betsy Centeno, University of California - Santa Cruz; Saskias Casanova, University of California - Santa Cruz*

"That Full Circle Connection:" Mentoring Future Educators through Service-Learning at a Hispanic-Serving Institution. *Kathryn Nagrotsky, University of Connecticut - Stamford; Jenifer Gaitan, Teachers College, Columbia University; Alyssa Hadley Dunn, University of Connecticut; Tracy Sinclair, University of Connecticut; Kenya Marie Overton, University of Connecticut; Ashanti Hall, University of Connecticut*

87.010. SIG-Law and Education Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Law and Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Opportunities and Challenges for Addressing Teacher-to-Student Bullying after Taiwan's New Legislation: A Conflicting Rationalities Analysis. *Jih-Syuan Lin, National Chung Hsing University; Mike Yuchuan Shen, National Chung Hsing University*

87.010. SIG-Leadership for School Improvement Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Leadership for School Improvement; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Development and Validation of an Instrument for Assessing Departmental Leadership in China. *Jia Zhang, Zhejiang University*

From Bureaucracy to Belonging: Transforming School Leadership for Adaptive Education among Native Americans. *James N. Onukwu, Washington State University*

Leadership Practices in Academically Successful Under-resourced Philippine Elementary Schools: A Qualitative Inquiry. *Ma Glenda Lopez Wui, Ateneo de Manila University; Enrique Nino P. Leviste, Ateneo de Manila University; Jessica Sandra R. Claudio, Ateneo de Manila University; Rosselle Trishia M. Reyes, Ateneo de Manila University*

School Leaders' Perspectives on Developing Inclusive and Equitable Schools. *Angela Voutier, Brandon University*
Research synthesis of principal system leadership from its birth to 2024: A narrative approach. *Cheng Jin, The Education University of Hong Kong; Junjun Chen, Education University of Hong Kong; Wendan XU, The Education University of Hong Kong*

87.010. SIG-Learning and Teaching in Educational Leadership Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Learning and Teaching in Educational Leadership; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

(Re)Imagining Principal Preparation Through Praxis: Integrating Problem-Based Learning and Reflective Practice in Educational Leadership. *Rachel Anna Kamnkhwani-Kaulembe, Boise State University*

87.010. SIG-Learning Environments Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Learning Environments; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Are more screens better? A study of the effects of classroom screens on student attention and learning outcomes based on eye movement evidence. *Aixia Li, LUDONG UNIVERSITY; Lu Li, The University of Ludong; liyan yu, Ludong University; 子群李, Ludong university*

Learning Through Making: Elementary Students' Perceptions of a STEM Makerspace Learning Environment. *Anthony George Timpano, American School in Taichung; Rachel Sarah Sheffield, Curtin University; Rekha Bhan Koul, Curtin University*

Unforgetting Static Histories: Educational Digital-Human Platform for Primary Online Programming Futures. *Hailiang Yang, East China Normal University; Hongji Deng, Beijing Normal University; Hao Zheng, East China Normal University; Wenxuan Zhang, East China Normal University; Weiyu Zhang, Beijing Normal University; Yonghe Wu, East China Normal University*

87.010. SIG-Learning Sciences Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Learning Sciences; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Characterizing Digging Deeper in Online Information Behavior. *Sky Galili, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev; Iris Tabak, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev*

Pedagogical Play in the Makery: Examining Puppet Use in an Elementary School Makerspace. *Robert Daniel Wachtel Pronovost, Stanford University*

87.010. SIG-Lesson Study Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Lesson Study; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

From Lesson Study to Collaborative Growth: Dialogic Pathways for Equitable Teacher Professional Learning.

Christina Chinas, Durham University

87.010. SIG-Measurement and Assessment in Higher Education Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Measurement and Assessment in Higher Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

From Diagnosis to Dialogue: A Knowledge-Augmented Framework for Generating Interpretable Feedback from Deep Knowledge Tracing. *Zhen Li, Central China Normal University; Chenxuan He, Central China Normal University*

87.010. SIG-Media, Culture, and Learning Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Media, Culture, and Learning; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Virtual World Environments And Intercultural Communication in Language Learning: A Research Synthesis. *Priscilla Tuffour, University of South Florida - Tampa; Sanghoon Park, University of South Florida*

87.010. SIG-Middle-Level Education Research Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Middle-Level Education Research; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Understanding School Belonging in the Middle Grades: A Multilevel Analysis of Predictors Among Young Adolescents. *Tonje Mari Molyneux, University of British Columbia; Jenna D. Shapka, University of British Columbia; Anusha Kassin, University of British Columbia; Eva Oberle, University of British Columbia*

87.010. SIG-Moral Development and Education Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Moral Development and Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

"What If She is Poor? What If She Looks Different From me?": Children's Integration of Race and Wealthy Status in Their Fair Distribution Decisions. *Jee Young Noh, Biola University; Kelly Min, Biola University*

87.010. SIG-Motivation in Education Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Motivation in Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Minute by Minute: Unfolding Patterns of Parental Behaviors in Math Homework Help. *Jiawen Wu, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Luxin Zhang, Teachers College, Columbia University; Yinuo Jia, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Eva M. Pomerantz, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Validation of the Korean Motivational Regulation Strategies Scale for Non-Traditional Adult Learners In Online Distance Learning. *Heoncheol Yun, Hankyong National University; Sanghoon Park, University of South Florida; Yongho Won, Hanyang University; Sukjin Kwon, Gukje Cyber University*

87.010. SIG-Multicultural/Multiethnic Education: Theory, Research and Practice Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Multicultural/Multiethnic Education: Theory, Research and Practice; Virtual iPresentation Only

Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

We Speak to All Students: Portraying Teachers' Language of Inclusivity. *Thomas Salsbury, Washington State University; Jihee Im, Washington State University; Eugenie Mainake, Washington State University*

From Marginalisation to Belongingness: Language and Well-being for Inclusive Education in South African Schools. *Margaret Funke Omidire, University of Pretoria; Shauib Abolakale Muhammed, University of Pretoria*

87.010. SIG-Music Education Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Music Education; Virtual iPresentation Only

Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Forced Nomadism in Thin Air: Music Teachers' Socioecological Burnout in Tibet. *Yuqi LIN, University of Macau; Qizong Yue, Southwest University; Katy Jeong Cheng Ho Weatherly, University of Macau*

87.010. SIG-Narrative Research Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Narrative Research; Virtual iPresentation Only

Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Breaking the Loop: A Narrative Inquiry of an International PhD Graduate in Academia. *Jiaxuan Zong, University of Maryland*

87.010. SIG-Online Teaching and Learning Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Online Teaching and Learning; Virtual iPresentation Only

Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Examining Instructor Social Presence and Student Outcomes in Higher Education: A Meta-Analysis. *Jing Song, Purdue University; Alexander J. Bowman, Purdue University; Zhuo Zhang, Towson University; Adrie A. Koehler, Purdue University; Yukiko Maeda, Purdue University; Jennifer C. Richardson, Purdue University*

The Relationships Between Community of Inquiry, Academic Procrastination, And Achievement Among Non-Traditional Online Students. *Sanghoon Park, University of South Florida; Yongho Won, Hanyang University; Sukjin Kwon, Gukje Cyber University; Heoncheol Yun, Hankyong National University*

Towards Equitable Online Learning: Gender, SES, Prior Experience, and Digital Literacy in Rural China. *Fengjiao Liu, University of Bristol*

87.010. SIG-Paulo Freire Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Paulo Freire; Virtual iPresentation Only

Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Compassionate Pedagogy as Strategic Practice: Advancing Educational Equity Through Historical Memory and Future-Oriented Teaching. *Jaclyn K. Rivard, University of Southern Mississippi*

87.010. SIG-Philosophical Studies in Education Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Philosophical Studies in Education; Virtual iPresentation Only

Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Revisiting Matthews's Criticism from the Perspective of Piaget's Genetic Epistemology. *Haoran Liu, East China Normal University*

87.010. SIG-Politics of Education Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Politics of Education; Virtual iPresentation Only

Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Insurgencies on the Discursive Plains: The End of the Concretized Myth of White Supremacy. *Ayan Abdulle, University of Toronto - OISE*

From Disruption to Imitation: Rethinking Innovation in the Charter School Movement. *Robert Niewiadomski, Fordham University*

87.010. SIG-Problem-Based and Project-Based Learning Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Problem-Based and Project-Based Learning; Virtual iPresentation Only

Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Reviving Cultural Heritage, Cultivating Creativity: Project-Based Learning in Inner Mongolia's Public Kindergartens. *Yuxin Zhang, University of Malaya; Yu Zhou, University of Manchester*

87.010. SIG-Qualitative Research Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Qualitative Research; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Confucian embodied knowing: Implications for reenvisioning qualitative methodologies. *Zitong Wei, China Women's University*

Words Speak for Themselves – Advocating for the Use of Documentary Data. *Dino Sossi, NYU, CUNY, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Unforgetting and Reimagining Belonging: A Duoethnography of International Faculty in a Midwestern PWL. *Somanita Kheang, Ball State University; Regina J. Giraldo-Garcia, Ball State University; Michael Takafor Ndemanu, Ball State University*

Human-AI Collaboration in Reflexive Thematic Analysis: A Case Study. *Yao Yang, Purdue University; Daniel Carpenter, Purdue University; Katie H Dufault, Purdue University; Craig Johnson, Purdue University; Anne Weiss, Purdue University*

87.010. SIG-Rasch Measurement Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Rasch Measurement; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Does Answer Option Positioning Lead to DIF in Reading Comprehension? An Analysis with Parametric Logistic Item Response Theory Model Trees. *Farshad Effatpanah Hesari, Technical University of Dortmund; Islamic Azad University, Mashhad Branch*

A Rasch Analysis of the Couples Satisfaction Index. *Colette A Norgard, University of Colorado - Denver; Tom Su, University of Colorado - Denver*

87.010. SIG-Research in Mathematics Education Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Research in Mathematics Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Portrayal of Female and Male Mathematicians in Theatrical Plays. *Emma LaPlace, Teachers College, Columbia University; Irina Lyublinskaya, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Psychometric Validation and Exploratory Path Analysis of the Chinese Math Attitudes Scale: A Single-Sample Study. *Run*

Wen, Xi'an Jiaotong-Liverpool University; Wenmin Zhao, University of Saint Joseph

Avoiding a New Math War: Harmonizing Tensions Between Mathematics Education and Special Education Over Disability. *Thomas E. Ricks, Louisiana State University*

How do math anxiety, parent involvement, and academic self-concept impact adolescent math achievement? *Anna Levy, Fordham University; Yi Ding, Fordham University*

87.010. SIG-Rural Education Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Rural Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Navigating Family-School Relationships in Rural Communities: A Scoping Review. *Abigail Stephan, Clemson University; Nora D. Hochstetter, Clemson University; Itumu Olaniran Akande, Clemson University; Verdah Rehan, Clemson University; Virginia Clark, Clemson University; Faiza M. Jamil, Clemson University*

87.010. SIG-School Community, Climate, and Culture Virtual Poster Session. SIG-School Community, Climate, and Culture; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Reimagining School Belonging Through the Eyes of Young Adolescents: A Mixed Methods Inquiry. *Tonje Mari Molyneux, University of British Columbia; Jenna D. Shapka, University of British Columbia; Anusha Kassan, University of British Columbia; Eva Oberle, University of British Columbia*

Measuring School Climate Through Parents' Eyes: Scale Adaptation and Validation. *Louise Clément, Université Laval; Caterina Mamprin, Université de Montréal; Patricia Vohl, Université Laval; Marie-Christine Rivest, Université du Québec en Outaouais; Marie-Michèle Roy, Université de Moncton; Romane Gauvreau, Université Laval*

87.010. SIG-Science Teaching and Learning Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Science Teaching and Learning; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

A Micro-Level Discourse-Based Description of Modeling-Based Learning in Kindergarten Science. *Loucas T. Louca, European University Cyprus; Melina Xení, Ministry of Education and Culture, Cyprus*

87.010. SIG-Sociology of Education Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Sociology of Education; Virtual iPresentation Only

Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Effects of Employment Support Program in Vocational High Schools in South Korea on Labor-Market Outcomes. *Mina Je, Korean Educational Development Institute(prior)*

87.010. SIG-Special and Inclusive Education Research Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Special and Inclusive Education Research; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Providing Services to All Students: Examining Teacher Awareness to Support LGBTQ+ Students with Disabilities. *Joseph A. Hogan, Kean University*

AAC Communication Partners' Knowledge of Abuse-Related Vocabulary Organization on AAC Devices. *Sarah Monaco, The College of New Jersey*

Inclusion of adults with Intellectual Development Disability in educational programs. *Heidi Flavian, Achva Academic College*

87.010. SIG-Stress, Coping, and Resilience Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Stress, Coping, and Resilience; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Individual and Contextual Factors Attributing to Teacher Stress Based on Academic Setting and Years of Experience. *Parul Acharya, Columbus State University; Lisa Lashley Freeman, Bibb County School District, Georgia*

School Principals Under Pressure: Mental Load, Job Autonomy, and Retention. *Marie-Christine Rivest, Université du Québec en Outaouais; Louise Clément, Université Laval*

A conceptual framework of principal resilience: Narrative review from 2005 to 2024 (Poster 55). *Wendan XU, The Education University of Hong Kong; Junjun Chen, Education University of Hong Kong; Cheng Jin, The Education University of Hong Kong*

87.010. SIG-Studying and Self-Regulated Learning Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Studying and Self-Regulated Learning; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Phase-Specific Effects of AI in Self-Regulated Learning: A Meta-Analysis of a Decade of Interventions. *Jun Xu, East China Normal University; Yuying Luo, Shanghai University; Chengliang Wang, Australian Catholic University; Hao Zheng, East China Normal University; Yonghe Wu, East*

China Normal University

87.010. SIG-Supervision and Instructional Leadership Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Supervision and Instructional Leadership; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

A (Very) Exploratory Study of Practicum Interactions and Their Impact on Teaching Performance. *Jamie H. Hamblin, Southern Utah University; Abbey Judd, Southern Utah University; William J. Davis, Southern Utah University*

87.010. SIG-Survey Research in Education Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Survey Research in Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Exploring Student Perspectives on Instructional Evaluations: A Qualitative Study of SPoI Participation and Feedback. *Elizabeth Templeton, Florida Gulf Coast University; Jenny Kerzetski, School District of Lee County; Jingshun Zhang, Florida Gulf Coast University*

87.010. SIG-Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Rethinking School-Based Substance Use Interventions: An Overview of Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analysis through Educational and Public Health Lenses. *Emily Jenkins, University of British Columbia; Mohammad Karamouzian, University of Toronto; Tonje Mari Molyneux, University of British Columbia; Dana Dmytro, University of British Columbia*

Does Technology-Based Learning Environment Promote Students' Self-Regulated Learning? A Meta-Analysis of Two Decades of Empirical Research. *Yinuo Li, university of bristol*

The Impact of Project-Based Learning on Achievement in Secondary Mathematics. *Angie Sostak, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

Exploring the influence of secure attachment on bullying behaviors. *Yihan Zhang, University of Macau; Yihui Wang, Shanghai Normal University; Juan Zhang, University of Macau*

87.010. SIG-Systems Thinking in Education Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Systems Thinking in Education; Virtual iPresentation Only

Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Evaluating the Homological Reasoning Levels of Senior Pre-service Middle School Science Teachers Using System Scenarios. *Ulku Seher Budak, Bogazici University; Gaye Defne Ceyhan, Bogazici University*

87.010. SIG-Teachers Work/Teacher Unions Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Teachers Work/Teacher Unions; Virtual iPresentation Only

Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Two Decades of Teacher Organizing in New Orleans: "We're On the Front Lines." *Riley Collins, University of California - Santa Cruz*

87.010. SIG-Technology as an Agent of Change in Teaching and Learning Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Technology as an Agent of Change in Teaching and Learning; Virtual iPresentation Only

Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

A Multi-Modal Analysis: Young Children's Spatial Skills While Using Educational Robots. *Simgė Cicek, Bogazici University; Duygu Umuthu, Bogazici University*

ICT Practices: Influence of ICT Preparedness, ICT Induction, and Teacher Self-Efficacy. *Chengcheng Li, The Open University of China; Shaoan Zhang, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Qingmin Shi, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*

Designing for Change: Integrating Generative AI into Pre-Service Literacy Pedagogy. *Shannon M. Kane, University of Maryland; Loren Jones, University of Maryland*

A Case for AI Literacy: Generated Images Reproducing Biases. *Matthew Duvall, University of Pennsylvania; Chen Wang, University of Pennsylvania*

A Systematic Review of Studies on the Use of Generative Artificial Intelligence Tools in PK-12 Education. *Lauren J. Woo, Arizona State University; Leanna Archambault, Arizona State University; Jered Borup, George Mason University*

Looking Beyond the Output: How Preservice Teachers Assess the Instructional Value of AI-Generated Formative Tasks. *Molly Li, University of Delaware; Leigh Hibbard, University of Delaware; Rachel A. Karchmer-Klein, University of Delaware*

H5P and Chinese College Students' Second Language Learning Engagement. *Yu Bi, Nantong Institute of Technology; Run Wen, Xi'an Jiaotong-Liverpool University*

ChatGPT and Lesson Planning in Early Childhood Education: Insights from Early Childhood Educators in the U.S. *Saigeetha Jambunathan, New Jersey City University; J.D*

Jayaraman, New Jersey City University

Mathematical Rigor, Mastery Learning, and Growth Mindset: A Content Analysis of IXL and Khan Academy. *Shalom Labkovski, Township of Ocean Schools; Vecihi Serbay Zambak, Monmouth University*

87.010. SIG-Technology, Instruction, Cognition & Learning Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Technology, Instruction, Cognition & Learning; Virtual iPresentation Only

Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Using Multi-Agent AI to Understand Cognitive Load and Emotional States in K-12 Math Learning. *Fan Zhang, University of Florida; Wanli Xing, University of Florida*

Unplugged Computational Thinking Activities and the Development of Primary Students' Self-Concept of Ability and Core Cognitive Skills: A Longitudinal Multi-Site Study in Austria. *Thomas Leitgeb, University of Education Burgenland; Wolfram Rollett, University of Oldenburg; Katja Scharenberg, Ludwig Maximilian University of Munich*

The Effects of SHAP Mechanism Disclosure on Trust in LLM Scoring Across Computational Thinking Levels. *Bingjie Zhang, The University of Hong Kong; Zhichun Liu, University of Hong Kong*

Beyond Single Scores: A Dual-Dimensional Assessment of Student Mastery in AI. *Zhen Li, Central China Normal University; Chenxuan He, Central China Normal University; Shangheng Du, East China Normal University*

87.010. SIG-Urban Learning, Teaching, and Research Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Urban Learning, Teaching, and Research; Virtual iPresentation Only

Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Stories of Trauma Among Teachers in Urban Classrooms. *Ami Ladhawala, University of Missouri - Kansas City; Candace M. Schlein, University of Missouri - Kansas City*

87.010. Research on Giftedness, Creativity and Talent Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Research on Giftedness, Creativity and Talent; Virtual iPresentation Only

Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Latent Classes of Ideation. *Süreyya Yörük, Bogazici University; Sedat Sen, Harran University*

87.010. Division C - Learning and Instruction / Division C - Section 3b: Technology-Based Environments Virtual Poster Session. Division C - Learning and Instruction;

Virtual iPresentation Only

Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Comparing the Effects of Intelligent Tutoring Systems and Traditional Instruction on Sight-Singing and Aural Skills.

TINGTING CHEN, Hunan International Economics University

Navigating the Boundary: English Language Teachers' Identity Perceptions in the Age of Artificial Intelligence Integration.

Nizar Bitar, The Max Stern Yezreel Valley College; Roseanne Kheir Farraj, Max Stern Yezre'el Valley College; Aya Onallah, The Max Stern Yezreel Valley College

Automating Meso-Level Classroom Analysis: An LLM-Based Approach Using the PTA Coding Framework. *Xiangfang Song, East China Normal University; Jingliang Kong, East China Normal University*

The Role of Complex Learning Interactions and Cognitive Load in Immersive Virtual Reality-based Chemistry Simulations. *Maral Karimi, University of Central Florida; Megan Wiedbusch, University of Central Florida; Cameron Marano, University of Central Florida; Annamarie Broshinan, University of Central Florida; Tara Brianna Delgado, University of Central Florida; Marta Sobocinski, University of Oulu; Natalie Blaize, University of Central Florida; Romina Jannotti, Trinity Preparatory School; Roger Azevedo, University of Central Florida*

87.010. Division C - Section 1d: Science Virtual Poster Session. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Virtual iPresentation Only

Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Exploring the Impact of STEM Education on Scientific Creativity and Reflective Thinking in Elementary Science Education. *Umran Atabas, Istanbul 29 Mayıs University; Gonul Sakiz, Marmara University*

Agency in the Climate Crisis: Reframing Science Education Through a Three-Lens Approach (Poster 4). *Giulia Tasquier, University of Bologna; Francesca Pongiglione, University Vita-Salute San Raffaele; Elena Claire Ricci, University of Verona*

87.010. Division E - Section 1: Counseling Virtual Poster Session. Division E - Counseling and Human Development; Virtual iPresentation Only

Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Unpacking beliefs about change and personal theories of change in counselors-in-training writing. *Beata M. Latawiec, Wichita State University; Jody Fiorini, Wichita State University; Jason Li, Wichita State University; Susan Bray,*

Wichita State University

87.010. Social and Emotional Learning Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Social and Emotional Learning; Virtual iPresentation Only

Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Understanding Misalignment Between Parents' and Children's Reports of Life Satisfaction. *Luofan Shu, Graduate Center - CUNY; Anastasiya A. Lipnevich, City University of New York*

87.010. Teaching History Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Teaching History; Virtual iPresentation Only

Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Learning to Contextualize: Modelling and Teaching a Complex Skill in History Education. *Marc-Andre Ethier, Université de Montréal; Kevin Péloquin, University of Montréal; David Lefrancois, University of Quebec - Outaouais; René Salem, University of Montréal*

87.010. Critical Perspectives on Early Childhood Education Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Critical Perspectives on Early Childhood Education; Virtual iPresentation Only

Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Worlds Away & Belly Aches: A Critical Content Analysis of Enclosure in Picturebooks (Poster 16). *Seneca Beth Miller, University of Arizona*

Unraveling the Colonial Illusion of Representation: Material Agency for Relational Ethics in Early Childhood Art Inquiry (Poster 12). *Hyewon Oh, Growing Place Ocean Park Early Childhood Education Center*

87.010. SIG-Graduate and Postdoctoral Education Across the Disciplines Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Graduate and Postdoctoral Education across the Disciplines; Virtual iPresentation Only

Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participants:

Facilitating Doctoral Student Development: Insights from the Student-Supervisor Relationship and Its Impacts. *Yingxiu Li, The Education University of Hong Kong; Wendan XU, The Education University of Hong Kong; Junjun Chen, Education University of Hong Kong*

Examine Power Dynamic: Equity and Mentorship in Transnational Doctoral Supervision. *Cheng Cui, Xi'an Jiaotong-Liverpool University; Qian Wang, Xi'an Jiaotong-*

Liverpool University; Jeong Jin Yu, Xi'an Jiaotong-Liverpool University; Martin Gough, University of Liverpool; Rong Yan, Xi'an Jiaotong-Liverpool University

87.010. Religion and Education Virtual Poster Session. SIG-Religion and Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

Incorporating Dialogic Education and the Traditional Halaqah Model in UAE Primary Islamic Studies Classrooms. *Arwa Al Qassim, University of Cambridge*

87.010. Division J - Section 1: Student Learning and Development in College and Beyond Virtual Poster Session. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Virtual iPresentation Only
Virtual Posters Exhibit Hall, Virtual Poster Hall; 7:45am to 3:00pm

Participant:

"I Wasn't Given These Experiences for Just Myself": Black Undergraduate Women's Purpose Development as Resistance and Self-Preservation at a Predominantly White Institution. *Jayla Moody Marshall, North Carolina State University*

Sunday, April 12th, 7:00 am

AERA Related Activities

88.010. Minority Fellows Mentoring Meeting With the Minority Fellowship Selection Committee Closed Meeting. AERA Related Activities; Governance Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 518;
7:00-9:15am

Chair: *George L. Wimberly, American Educational Research Association*

Committee Sessions

88.011. AERA Graduate Student Resource Center (Day 5). Graduate Student Council; Networking Center
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 502B;
7:00am to 10:00pm

Sunday, April 12th, 7:45 am

Governance Meetings and Events

89.001. AERA Professional Development and Training Committee: Closed Meeting. AERA Governance;

Governance Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 513;
7:45-9:15am

Chair: *Courtney A. Bell, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Committee Sessions

89.010. Beyond the Handshake: Building Meaningful Mentoring Networks in Academia and Beyond. Graduate Student Council; Invited Speaker Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 402A;
7:45-9:15am

Chair: *Cammie Justus-Smith, Virginia Commonwealth University*
Panelists: *Nora Dominguez, University of New Mexico; Kathleen Mary Cowin, Washington State University - Tri-Cities; Edith P. Middleton, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Division Sessions

89.011. Speculative Methodologies and Anti-Racist Curricular Practice: Building Curricular Futures Beyond Anti-Blackness. Division B - Curriculum Studies; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304A;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Beyond the Sacred Timeline: A Curricular Pluriverse Framework for Understanding Black Educational Temporalities. *Stephanie R. Toliver, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

(Re)Storying Encounters With Anti-Blackness In Early Childhood Education: Thinking With Refusal. *Fikile Nxumalo, University of Toronto - OISE; Veronica Pacini-Ketchabaw, Western University*

We Need Black Girl Environmental Futures. *Maya Revell, University of Oregon*

Cultivating AntiRacist Curricular Ecologies: Imagining Inclusive Educational Futurities as an Endlessly Evolving Endeavor. *Jerry L. Rosiek, University of Oregon*

Chair: *Ezekiel J. Dixon-Roman, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Discussant: *Ezekiel J. Dixon-Roman, Teachers College, Columbia University*

89.012. Teacher Identity Development: Expanding Conceptualizations to Account for Changing and Challenging Contexts. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Symposium
Westin Bonaventure, Level 3, Avalon; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Teacher Identity Development Within Complex Sociocultural and Political Contexts: The Dynamic Systems Model of Role Identity. *Joanna K. Garner, Old Dominion University; Avi Kaplan, Temple University*

Facilitating Mathematics Teacher Identity Development Through Holistic Personalized Coaching. *Dionne Cross Francis, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Kathryn Habib, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Pavneet Kaur Bharaj, California State University - Long Beach; Boran Yu, University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill; Anina Mahmud, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Brit'ny Pinkney, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Ji Y. Hong, University of Arizona*

From Awareness to Action: Critical Teacher Identity Development. *Ji Y. Hong, University of Arizona; Dionne Cross Francis, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Soojeong Lee, University of Arizona; Travis Jon Dean, University of Arizona; Jing Zhao, Educational Psychology; Yijia Chen, University of Arizona; Lijie Liu, University of Arizona; Nitika Mehta, University of Arizona; Paul A Schutz, University of Arizona*

Teacher Identity and Political Instruction in Turbulent Times. *Wayne Journell, University of North Carolina - Greensboro*

Teacher Identity Development and Black Homeschooling Parents: Centering Black Homeschool Narratives. *Meca R. Williams-Johnson, Georgia Southern University*

Emerging and Potential Methodologies in Research on Mathematics-Related Teacher Identity. *Sonja Lutovac; Andreas Ebbelind, Linnaeus University; Tracy Helliwell, University of Bristol*

Chairs: *Ji Y. Hong, University of Arizona; Dionne Cross Francis, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Paul A Schutz, University of Arizona*

Discussant: *Paul A Schutz, University of Arizona*

89.013. Advancing Equity and Cultural Responsiveness in Counselor Education and Practice. Division E - Counseling and Human Development; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 303A;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

RaceCrits in Counselor Education: Pedagogy for Unforgetting Histories and (Re)Imagining Client Futures. *Demetrius Cofield, The Ohio State University*

The Hidden Curriculum: How Cultural Silencing Shapes Supervision. *Zoya A McCants, St. John's University*

The Role of Student-Counselor Interactions and School Connectedness in Promoting College Enrollment for English Learners. *Hyunhee Kim, Johns Hopkins University; Jungnam Kim, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Julia Bryan, Pennsylvania State University*

Understanding Support for Marginalized Students through the Lens of School Counselors. *Na Mi Bang, Indiana University*

Indianapolis; Valerie Couture, University of Central Arkansas

White Counselors' exposure to Black individuals and their counseling effectiveness with Black clients. *Fanghui Zhao, Seattle University; Jeffrey A. Hayes, Pennsylvania State University*

Chair: *Sandra Barrueco, The Catholic University of America*

Discussant: *Sandra Barrueco, The Catholic University of America*

89.014. Genealogies of Black Possibility within 20th Century

Black Education. Division F - Historical Inquiry in Education; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 306A;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

"The Dissemination of the Truth": Black Educators' Continued Fight for Social Studies Curricula, 1940-1970. *Ziyen Curtis, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Laboratory Physics: The Entanglement of Physics and Black Liberation. *Ayshea Banes, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

"By Far the Greatest Stimulus": Schoolchildren, Negro History Week, and an Inherited Legacy. *Gloria J. Ashaolu, Michigan State University*

"Unsuited for the Times": Edward K. Weaver's (1913-1984) Conceptual Personae and Black Liberatory Science Education. *Curtis O'Dwyer, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Chair: *Jessica Lee Stovall, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Discussant: *Darion A. Wallace, Stanford University*

89.015. MSI's in the Social Context of Education. Division G -

Social Context of Education; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 303B;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Servingness and Belonging in an Era of Extremism: Countering Bias at Hispanic-Serving Institutions. *Christian A. Bracho, California State University - Long Beach*

From Lived Experience to Systemic Change: Advancing Equity in a Minority Serving Institution. *K. Kanoho Hosoda, University of Hawaii - Manoa*

Whiteness in the Minoritizing Institutions: How white Emotionalities Hinder Progress in Minoritizing Institutions. *Cheryl E. Mattias, University of San Diego*

Elevating Cross-Racial Solidarities With/in Institutionally Hostile Spaces: Lessons Learned from an all-AAPI AANAPISI Team. *Rachel Endo, University of Washington - Tacoma*

From PWI to HBCU: Navigating the Intersection of Identity, Equity, and Institutional Transformation in Higher Education. *Aaron R. Campbell, University of Missouri*

Chair: *Christian A. Bracho, California State University - Long Beach*

Discussant: *Rachel Endo, University of Washington - Tacoma*

89.016. Thriving in Context: Exploring Dimensions of Variation in Equity-Driven Partnership Research.

Division H - Research, Evaluation and Assessment in Schools; Symposium
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Hancock Park West; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Inclusion in an Anti-DEIA Time: Lessons Learned from a Partnership Using a Critical Inclusion Framework. *Rachel Saperstein McClam, Johns Hopkins University; Alexandra Shelton, Johns Hopkins University; Rebecca A. Cruz, Johns Hopkins University; Lindi Shepard, Johns Hopkins University; Sarah A Caroleo, Brown University; Matthew L. Love, San Jose State University; Christina Davis, Montgomery County Public Schools*

From Tinkering with Disability Proportions to Building Systems for Thriving: Leveraging Spatial Inquiry in RPPs. *Alfredo J. Artiles, Stanford University; Allison Firestone, San Francisco Unified School District; Laticia Errie De Erving, San Francisco Unified School District; Mauricha Robinson, San Francisco Unified School District; Rebecca A. Cruz, Johns Hopkins University; Chris Lukinbeal, University of Arizona; Hari Subramonyam, Stanford University; Michelle Casas, Stanford University; Lavar Edmonds, Stanford University; Isun Malekghassemi, Johns Hopkins University; Yura Oh, Stanford University*

Banned Words, Living Practice: Enacting Inclusion, Equity, and Systemic Transformation in a Time of Dread. *Aydin Bal, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Dywayne Hinds, Pinellas County Schools; Keisha Albritton, Pinellas County Schools; Dominique Dudley, Pinellas County Schools; Elizabeth Schrader, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Chair: *Laura P. Wentworth, California Education Partners*

Discussant: *Paula Arce-Trigatti, National Network of Education Research-Practice Partnerships*

89.017. Beyond Lortie: New sociological perspectives on professions and their application to teaching.

Division I - Education in the Professions; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Plaza III; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Teaching is Both Public and Professional: How Can it be Both? *Joshua L. Glazer, The George Washington University*

A Degree of Choice: The Role of Occupations in Educational Decision-Making. *Maya Kaul, University of Pennsylvania; Ellen Bryer, Brown University*

Towards a Public, Relational Notion of Educational Professionalism. *Jal David Mehta, Harvard University; Krista Galleberg, Harvard University*

The 'Double-Edged Sword' of Teacher Professionalism: Fusing Expertise and Democratic Conceptions to Rebuild Public

Trust. *Ayelet Becher, The Open University of Israel*
The Rise (and Fall?) of Professionalism: Logics of Work in Popular Discourse About Teachers in the United States, 1990-2019. *Matthew Shirrell, The George Washington University*

Chair: *Joshua L. Glazer, The George Washington University*

Discussant: *Pamela L. Grossman, University of Pennsylvania*

89.018. Access and Experiences in STEM.

Division J - Postsecondary Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum G; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Belonging and agency: High-achieving undergraduate women of colour navigating STEM. *Nichole Powell, Emory University; Dalen Arthur, University of Ontario Institute of Technology; Lonimi Christina Ayekun, University of Guelph; Robyn Ruttenberg-Rozen, University of Ontario Institute of Technology*

Exploring How Future Time Perspective Shapes Current Motivation and Choices Among Undergraduate STEM Students. *Joseph Romero-Reyes, Iowa State University; Angela Ebreo, University of Michigan; Minso Choi, The Ohio State University; Chetna Kumari, University of Michigan*

Exploring how Students who Experience Illness, Injury, or Dis/ability Persist in STEM. *Catherine A. Manly, Fairleigh Dickinson University; Alyse C. Hachey, University of Texas - El Paso; Claire Wladis, Borough of Manhattan Community College*

"I Don't Want to Be a Martyr": Career Disruption for Space Sciences Graduate Students. *Radomir Ray Mitic, College of William & Mary; Bingqing Wu, College of William & Mary; Maire Brandenburg, University of North Dakota*

Learning Power: A Poststructural Analysis of Academic Help-Seeking in STEM Gateway Coursework. *Amy Jane Rodgers Awtrey, University of Cincinnati; Amy N. Farley, University of Cincinnati; Christopher M. Swoboda, University of Cincinnati; Jarrod E. Druery, University of Cincinnati*

Discussant: *Jialin Yan, University of Rochester*

89.019. Construyendo Caminos: Expanding Access and Pathways for Latinx/a/o/e Students.

Division J - Postsecondary Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum F; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Rural Latinx Youth Choosing the Community College Pathway. *Mayra Puente, University of California - Santa Barbara; Lupita Romo-González, University of California - Santa Barbara; Marlene Lopez Torres, University of California - Santa Barbara; Melissa Romero, University of California - Santa Barbara*

Using Improvement Science to Explore the Importance of a

College-going Community in a Latinx Neighborhood.
Graciela Ortiz, California State University - Fullerton;
Chenoa S. Woods, California State University, Office of the
Chancellor

Beyond Racialized School Barriers: Latinx (Im)migrant
Families Navigating and Reimagining Dual Credit Access.
Henedina Tavares, University of Washington

Reframing Transfer Choice: Centering the Lived Experiences
of Latina/o/x Students in the Transfer Decision-Making
Process. *Ivan Valdovinos, San Diego Community College*
District

Chair: *Reyna M. Flores, Rosa Educational Research and*
Consulting, LLC

Discussant: *Angel D. Gonzalez, California State University -*
Fresno

89.020. Battling Burnout: Time, Tech, and Teacher Wellbeing.

Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper
Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 1;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

An Anxious Teacher: The Links between Teacher Math
Anxiety and Student Achievement. *NaYoung Hwang,*
University of New Hampshire; Suzanne E. Graham,
University of New Hampshire; Mark Berends, University of
Notre Dame

Effectiveness of Emotion Regulation-Related Interventions for
Teachers: A Meta- Analysis. *Fang Wang, University of*
South Carolina; Juan Wang, University of South Carolina;
Yukang Xue, University at Albany - SUNY; Xinyu Li,
University at Albany - SUNY; Qi Sun, University at Albany -
SUNY; Ruiqin Gao, University of South Carolina; Kala
Dunn, University of South Carolina

Empowerment or Overload? The Nonlinear Effects of Digital
Technology on Teachers' Work Time Allocation. *SICHENG*
LIU, East China Normal University

Heavy Hours: Secondary ELA teachers experiences and
perceptions of time and work intensification. *Kristal*
Parrish, Texas A&M University; Radhika Viruru, Texas
A&M University; Sharon D. Matthews, Texas A&M
University

In-Service Educators' Meaning-Making and Experiences with
Mindful Outdoor Engagements. *Jessica Fundalinski,*
Syracuse University; Amanda Kingston, Syracuse University

Chair: *Sheila Stefany Coli, District 428*

Discussant: *Sheila R. Vaidya, Drexel University*

89.021. Building Bridges & Capacity: Equitable Professional Development for Multilingual Learner Achievement.

Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper
Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 8;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Building Bridges Through Assessment: Transforming Teacher
Practice for Multilingual Learner Thriving. *Gift Onwubuya,*
University of Utah; Josephine Amoakoh, University of Utah;
Veronica E. Valdez, University of Utah

Cultivating Psychological Capital: Inservice Teachers'
Exploration of Asset-Based Practices for Multilingual
Learners. *Kwangok Song, University of Kansas; Rachel*
Kook, University of Kansas; Lonna Sue Summers, University
of Kansas; Tong Xu, University of Kansas

Predictors of Self-Efficacy Among Secondary Teachers in
Multicultural and Multilingual Classrooms Using a Machine
Learning Approach. *Eunjee Jang, University of Wisconsin -*
River Falls; Young Sik Seo, University at Buffalo - SUNY;
Bong Gee Jang, Syracuse University

The Impact of a Professional Development Program Focused
on Multilingual Learners for K-12 Educators. *Bita Moradi,*
University of Delaware; Adrian Pasquarella, University of
Delaware; Nigel Caplan, University of Delaware; Samantha
Jo Shewchuk, University of Delaware; Jamie Janick,
University of Delaware

Discussant: *Danielle Igra, Brandeis University*

89.022. Centering Teachers' Equitable Participation in Professional Development: Partnership Approaches in Chile and the U.S. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Symposium

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 9;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Creating Conditions for Teacher Leadership through a Chilean
RPP in Mathematics Education. *Florencia Gomez*
Zaccarelli, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile;
Bárbara Zoro, Pontificia Universidad Católica de
Valparaiso; Horacio Solar, Pontificia Universidad Católica
de Chile

Research Practice Partnerships in Chile: Building a Collective
Improvement Mindset from Teacher's Voice. *Monica*
Cortez, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Valparaiso;
Felipe Aravena, Pontificia Universidad Católica de
Valparaiso; Isabel Zett, Pontificia Universidad Católica de
Valparaiso

Empowering Teacher Learning Through Lesson Study: Insights
from a Research-Practice Partnership. *Marley Angelita*
Murrell, Stanford University; Meghan Smith Durkin,
Stanford University; Hilda Borko, Stanford University

Tensions and Teacher Agency in Adaptive Professional
Development. *Christina Kimmerling, University of*
California - Irvine; Rossella Santagata, University of
California - Irvine; Patricia Fuentes Acevedo, University of
California - Irvine

Chairs: *Patricia Fuentes Acevedo, University of California -*
Irvine; Florencia Gomez Zaccarelli, Pontificia Universidad
Católica de Chile

Discussants: *Beth A. Herbel-Eisenmann, Michigan State University; Elham Kazemi, University of Washington*

89.023. Pedagogies Under Pressure: Navigating Constraint, Fear, and Resistance in Education. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 6;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Choosing "Safe": Political Fear and the Erasure of Current Histories in Preservice Teacher Practice. *Amanda Man, University of Delaware; Joy Esboldt, University of Delaware; Bonnie Lewis, University of Delaware; Soo Bin Jang, University of Delaware*

Places of Learning/Places of Violence: Teaching in the Wake of a School Shooting. *H. James Garrett, University of Georgia; Rebecca Cooper Geller, University of Georgia*

Teaching Through Trouble: Making Sense of Restrictive Educational Climates in Pursuit of New Futures. *Sabrina Leigh Caldwell, University of South Alabama*

Unforgetting ELA's Role in Climate Education: Florida Teachers Navigating Restrictive Politics to Imagine Justice-Centered Futures. *Alexandra Panos, University of South Florida; Katharine Hull, University of South Florida*

Chair: *Amanda Man, University of Delaware*

Discussant: *Covel Audia Hall-Golding, University of Victoria*

89.024. Complex Contestation: Understanding the Structures and Actors that Manage Dissent in the U.S. K-12 Political Landscape. Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 10; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Democracy For What and For Whom?: The Possibilities and Challenges of K-12 School Boards. *James C. Bridgeforth, University of Delaware; Julie A. Marsh, University of Southern California; Akunna Faith Uka, University of Southern California; Laura Steen Mulfinger, University of Southern California; Jacob Alonso, University of Southern California*

Right Place, Right Time: The Democratic Challenges of Highly Privatized and Decentralized Education Governance. *Amanda Lu, Georgetown Public Policy Institute*

A Promise Unfulfilled: How Title VI is Used to Remedy Racial Discrimination in School Practices. *Rachel M. Perera, The Brookings Institution; Victor Cadilla, North Carolina State University*

Interpreting the Crisis of School Choice: Conjunctural Analysis and the Democratic Project of Public Education. *Talia S. Leibovitz, University of California - Berkeley*

Chair: *Kaylee T. Matheny, Stanford University*

Discussant: *Alexandra J. Freidus, University of Connecticut*

SIG Sessions

89.025. Creando Senderos en Comunidad: Working Towards Lifelong Language Learning with Latine Communities. SIG-Bilingual Education Research; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304C;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Reclaiming Language Histories for Justice: Preparing Latinx Educators for Secondary Dual Language Bilingual Education. *Massiel Zaragoza, University of Illinois at Chicago*

A Future That Contrasts the Past: Latina Teachers Called to Dual Language Bilingual Education. *Melizabeth Santos, Dominican University*

Power Dynamics of Belonging and Rejection at School for Spanish Heritage Speakers. *Lidia Aguilera, University of Illinois at Chicago*

Platicando con Padres de Nuestra Comunidad: Insights into Latine Parents' Language Goals. *Nancy Domínguez-Fret, Northern Illinois University; Yaniz Rodriguez, Northern Illinois University; Ramona Alcalá, University of Illinois at Chicago; Megan Tzeitel Marshall, University of Chicago; P. Zittlali Morales, University of Illinois at Chicago*

¿Cómo Se Dice Queer en Spanish? How Queer Chicana Educators Facilitate Affirming Bilingual Queer Curriculums. *Jodi Aguilar, University of Illinois at Chicago*

Chair: *Lydia A Saravia, DePaul University*

Discussant: *Joanna Maravilla, Lewis University*

89.026. Curriculum, Memory, and the Puerto Rican Diaspora: Creating Futures Beyond Erasure. SIG-Critical Issues in Curriculum and Cultural Studies; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304B;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Placemaking Through and Beyond the Ivory Towers and Decolonial Curricular Possibilities for Diasporican Futurities. *Daicy Diaz-Granados, Center for Puerto Rican Studies*

DiaspoFuturism through the Puerto Rican Archives: Unforgetting the Past to Build Alternative Futures in Education. *Carmin Quijano, Hunter College*

Curriculum as Diasporican Continuity: Pedagogical Commitments Toward Educational Futurity. *Francisco Medina, John Jay College of Criminal Justice*

Chair: *Francisco Medina, John Jay College of Criminal Justice*

Discussant: *Jordan Bell, Erikson Institute*

89.027. Voices of Advocacy: Family and Caregiver Perspectives on Disability in Education. SIG-Disability Studies in Education; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 511AB;

7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Experienced and Unprepared: A Parent-Educator Journey of Advocacy, Struggle, and Hope. *Cristina C. Santamaria Graff, Indiana University - Indianapolis; Román Graff, Ball State University*

“Inclusion is Non-Negotiable”: Resistance, Identity and Agency Among Parents of Children with Disabilities. *Eileen Cardona Osieja, Montclair State University; Priya Lalvani, Montclair State University*

Whose Voices Are Heard? A Twenty-Year Scoping Review of Caregiver Advocacy in Special Education. *Lydia L Ocasio-Stoutenburg, Pennsylvania State University; Azaria I. Cunningham, Boston University; Yuchen Yang, Pennsylvania State University*

Mothering as Politicized Action Through Identity: Expanding DisCrit Mothering Through Collective Autoethnography. *Saili S. Kulkarni, San Jose State University; Katie Mae McCabe, Buffalo State University - SUNY; Gabrielle Elizabeth Bernal, California State University - Monterey Bay; Benikia Kressler, California State University - Fullerton; Lilly Padia, Erikson Institute; Laurie Gutmann Kahn, Moravian University*

Chair: *Kristin Vogel-Campbell, North Point Educational Service Center*

Discussant: *Jing Su, University of California - Santa Barbara*

89.028. Approaches to Trauma-Informed Teaching in Early Childhood Education: Responding to Childhood Adversity Through Pedagogical Change. SIG-Early Education and Child Development; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Georgia I;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Embedding Trauma-Informed Care into an Early Childhood Special Education Program. *Catherine Corr, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Leveraging FEBA and SMART-TI Tools to Support Trauma-Sensitive Pedagogy in Early Childhood Classrooms. *Christy Tirrell-Corbin, University of Maryland; Carlomagno Panlilio, Pennsylvania State University; Claudia Kruzik, University of Maryland*

Tools for Transformative Practice: A Serious Game for Trauma-Informed Early Education. *Alysse Loomis, University of Utah; Ashley Guajardo, University of Utah; Arjun Shivakumar, University of Utah; Rose McLaughlin, University of California - Davis; Kristine Campbell, University of Utah*

Chair: *Christy Tirrell-Corbin, University of Maryland*

Discussant: *Carlomagno Panlilio, Pennsylvania State University*

89.029. Developing Faculty as Teacher-Scholars. SIG-Faculty Teaching, Evaluation, and Development; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 2;

7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Better Supporting Contingent, VITAL Faculty: Insights from Previous Delphi Award Winners. *KC Culver, University of Alabama; Adrianna Kezar, University of Southern California*

Examining How Work-Life Balance Relates to Motivation Among International Faculty in North America. *Bijaya Shrestha, University of North Dakota; Muhammad Salahuddin, University of North Dakota; Nathan C. Hall, Government of Canada; Robert H. Stupnisky, University of North Dakota*

Faculty Ambassadors: Towards a Professional Development Model for Academic Diplomacy. *Laura Cruz, Pennsylvania State University; Lisa A Lambert Snodgrass, Purdue University*

89.030. Engagement Is a Practice: Rethinking Equity in School-Community Partnerships. SIG-Family, School, Community Partnerships; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum J;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Talking together: Expanding Practice-Based Teacher Education Through Authentic Family Communication Scenarios for Family-School Collaboration. *Lightning Jay, Binghamton University - SUNY; Naorah Rimkunas, Binghamton University - SUNY*

Implementing Critical Simulations (CritSIMs): Praxis toward Reparative Futures in Teacher Education. *MaryBeth Yerdon, SUNY - College at Cortland; Chelsea Stinson, Binghamton University - SUNY*

Approximations of Communication: Comparing Two Approaches for Family Communication Preparation in Preservice Teacher Education. *Lightning Jay, Binghamton University - SUNY; MaryBeth Yerdon, SUNY - College at Cortland; Naorah Rimkunas, Binghamton University - SUNY*

Becoming With: Supporting Future Teachers and School Communities Through Collaborative Engagement. *Janine Al-Aseer, University of Tennessee; Megan Mundi, University of Tennessee*

Impacts of a Parent Mentor Program for Parent Classroom Volunteers. *Alexa Rayas, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Kevin Hall, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Nessrine Machaka, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Sam Hall, NIA Inc.; Nidia Ruedas-Gracia, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Elizabeth B. Dyer, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Christina Krist, Stanford University*

Chair: *Holly M. Kreider, National Association for Family, School and Community Engagement*

Discussant: *Holly M. Kreider, National Association for Family, School and Community Engagement*

89.031. Future-Oriented Dialogues on AI in Education. SIG-Instructional Technology; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Santa Barbara C; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

A decade later: Students' privacy perceptions of learning analytics. *Clara Schumacher, University of Potsdam; Dirk Ifenthaler, University of Mannheim*

Generative learning and generative AI: Outsourcing, augmenting or interfering with cognitive effort in learning. *Stephanie Moore, University of New Mexico; Victor Law, University of New Mexico; Lindsey White, The University of New Mexico; Kanchana Konara Mudiyansele, University of New Mexico; S. Pil Kang, University of New Mexico; Amir Hedayati Mehdiabadi*

Identifying Research Trends and Themes in Artificial Intelligence in Education: A Topic Modeling Approach. *Masoud Askarnia, Texas Tech University; Jongpil Cheon, Texas Tech University; Fethi A. Inan, Texas Tech University*

Evaluating an AI Tool for Researchers: Do the Benefits Outweigh the Risks? *Michael Ahlf, University of Houston; Sara G. McNeil, University of Houston*

Faculty-Led GenAI Interventions and Student Learning: A Three-level Meta-Analytic Study. *Katherine Jiawen Ren, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Ayesha Sadaf, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Judson Macdonald, University of North Carolina at Charlotte; Delandrus Lenet Ieashea Seales, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Ji Yae Bong, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Chuang Wang, University of North Carolina - Charlotte*

Chair: *Rick J. Voithofer, The Ohio State University*

89.032. Analyzing educational inequalities in the past for a better future: successful interventions to reverse them. SIG-International Studies; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 301B; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Reversing Inequalities in Education. A Primer for Inclusive Evidence Informed Learning Environments. *Simona Sankalaite, Public Policy and Management Institute*

Linguistic Capital, Rights, and Resistance. A Systematic Literature Review of Minority-Language Educational Inequalities. *Martin Brown, Dublin City University*

The policy relevance of recent longitudinal panel and cohort surveys of primary and secondary schools. *Dragana Avramov, Population and Social Policy Consultants*

Educational Inequalities and Good Practices for Students with Migrant Background: literature review and research results. *Tiziana Chiappelli, Università degli Studi di Siena; Sabina Leoncini, Università degli Studi di Siena*

From Vulnerability to Resilience: Educational Trajectories of Success Through Successful School Interventions. *Garazi*

Lopez de Aguilera, University of Barcelona

Chair: *Erica Rosenfeld Halverson, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Discussant: *Miguel Ángel Pulido-Rodríguez, Ramon Llull University*

89.033. Reimagining Belonging and Justice in K–12 Education: Centering Latine Students, Families, and Communities. SIG-Latina/o/x Research Issues; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum I; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

A Systematic Review of La Representación of Latine Students and Families in School Psychology Research. *Monica Romero, University of Texas at Austin; Elizabeth M Camarena, University of Illinois Chicago; Mariana Davila, University of Texas at Austin; Mayra A. Gaona, University of Illinois at Chicago*

Mexican Migrant Mothers' Hidden Narratives of Educational Navigation in Rural Idaho: "Es lo único que yo puedo hacer, convivir con ellos..." *Mariza Fernandez, Homedale School District #370; Eulalia Gallegos Buitron, Oregon Department of Education*

"No nos podemos desahogar en casa": Schooling and Wellbeing Among Recently-arrived, Unaccompanied Central American-origin Adolescents. *Jessica Trejos, City University of New York*

"What We Want From Our Principals": Latinx Parent Visions for School Leadership. *Maria Del Carmen Unda, University of Texas at Austin; Eligio Martinez, Cal Poly Pomona; Estela Lopez, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Youth at the Margins of the School: Latin American Immigrants Navigating U.S. Public Education. *Zaira Magana Carbajal, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Chair: *Eligio Martinez, Cal Poly Pomona*

Discussant: *Rosie Ojeda, California Polytechnic State University - San Luis Obispo*

89.034. Well-Being as Foundational to Women of Color Efforts for Equity and Social Justice Leadership. SIG-Leadership for Social Justice; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Level 2, Echo Park; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Educational Equity Leaders' Well-Being as Essential for Collective Thriving. *Ditra Backup, University of Maryland; Meghan Comstock, University of Maryland; Dayna Muniz, University of Pennsylvania; Deborah Euzebio, University of Maryland*

School Leadership Matters for Retaining Black Women Teachers. *Regina Lynn Seabrook, University of Minnesota*
Finding Strength Among Others: Women of Color School Principals' Use of Networks to Support Their Leadership. *Osly J. Flores, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Carole R. Collins Ayanlaja, Eastern Illinois University*

Sacred And Restorative Haven: A Multi-Case Study of Black Women Leading in Educational Facilities Management.

Winnie Kwofie, Texas Tech University

Restorative Self-healing from the Trauma Within:

Collaborative Autoethnographies of Two Black Women Leaders in Education. *Nicole Williams Browning, California State University - East Bay; Winnie Kwofie, Texas Tech University*

89.035. Designing for Affect and Embodiment: Ethical Attunements in the Futuring of Education. SIG-Learning Sciences; Symposium
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, La Cienega; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Interviewing as Embodied and Affective Learning Contexts.

Shivani Dave, University of California - Los Angeles; Lindsay Lindberg, University of California - Los Angeles

Representational Improvisation: Collective Ideation at the Intersection of Embodiment and Affect. *Corey Brady, Southern Methodist University; Lauren Vogelstein, Teachers College, Columbia University; Tessaly Jen, Vanderbilt University*

Reframing youth's embodied and affective resistance to an outdoor environment as a resource for learning. *Tessaly Jen, Vanderbilt University; Heidi Carlone, Vanderbilt University*

Affect and Embodiment in Everyday Pedagogical Designs:

Creating Sites of Possibility through Reflections on Multimodal Research Trajectories. *Ananda M. Marin, University of California - Los Angeles; Inmaculada Maria Garcia Sánchez, University of California - Los Angeles*

"Should We Move the Worm?": Designing Learning for Ethical Attunement through Affect and Embodiment. *Jordan D. Sherry-Wagner, University of Washington - Bothell; Miguel Angel Garcia-Bocanegra, Northwestern University; Carrie T. Tzou, University of Washington - Bothell; Megan Bang, Northwestern University*

Embodying Physics: Reconceptualizing Science Learning as an Embodied, Relational, and Culturally Sustaining Practice.

Dionne N. Champion, University of Florida; Folashade Cromwell Solomon; Machienvee Lammey, TERC

Chair: *Angela N. Booker, University of California - San Diego*

Discussants: *Shirin Vossoughi, Northwestern University; Meg Elena Escudé, University of California - Berkeley*

89.036. Collective Memory-Work for Unforgetting Histories and Imagining Futures: A Feminist, Collective Approach to Inquiry. SIG-Narrative Research; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Georgia II; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

"You won't colonize my values": Collective memory-work as communal healing praxis. *Bisola A. Wald, University of Minnesota; Keitha-Gail Martin-Kerr, University of*

Minnesota; Colleen Clements, University of Minnesota
"She didn't feel bad at all": Rewriting in Collective Memory-Work as a Site of Rupture. *Peng Nelson, University of Minnesota; Yilin Wei, University of Minnesota; Kelly O'Brien, University of Minnesota*
Being and Doing Collective Memory-Work Together as an Embodied Praxis. *Angela Coffee, Century College; Colleen Clements, University of Minnesota; Erin Beeman Stutelberg, Salisbury University*

"And now what?": Agitating Collectivity in Collective Memory-Work. *Anna Schick, University of Wisconsin - River Falls; Emina Buzinkic, Institute for Development and International Relations*

Chair: *Colleen Clements, University of Minnesota*

Discussant: *Erin Beeman Stutelberg, Salisbury University*

89.037. The Black Church Ain't Dead! A Revival on the Educational Legacy of the Black Church. SIG-Research
Focus on Black Education; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 306B; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Historic Role of Black Clergy as Public Intellectuals and Community Educators. *David Jason Childs, Northern Kentucky University*

"The Black Church Changed My Life!": Can I Testify? *Terrelle B. Sales, Pepperdine University*

Testimony as a Spiritual Literacy: Pedagogies of the Black Church. *Jamila Lyiscott, University of Massachusetts - Amherst; Jasmine Hoskins, Urban Dove*

Black Worldmaking in Worship: Pedagogical Lessons from the Aesthetic Life of the Black Church. *Justin A. Coles, University of Massachusetts - Amherst*

Black Church Pedagogy: An Assets-based Approach to Education Is Still Alive. *Gwendolyn Thompson McMillon, Oakland University*

Afrolantica: Black Boys' Experiences with Radical Black Love and Single Consciousness in a Christian African American Boarding School. *Evan Willis, University of North Carolina - Charlotte*

Chair: *Amber Neal-Stanley, Purdue University*

Discussant: *Amber Neal-Stanley, Purdue University*

89.038. Where in the World are World Languages? SIG-Second Language Research; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum A; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Where is World Language Education in Hispanic Linguistics? *Aris M. Clemons, University of Tennessee*

Where is World Language Education in Teacher Education? *Tasha Austin, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

Where is World Language Education in Language Pedagogy? *L.J. Randolph, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Chair: *Tasha Austin, University at Buffalo - SUNY*
Discussant: *Aris M. Clemons, University of Tennessee*

89.039. Equity, Justice, and Transformation in Special and Inclusive Education. SIG-Special and Inclusive Education Research; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum H; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Educational Redlining in Special Education: Establishing New Civil Rights Protections for Students of Color With/Out Disabilities. *Nicholas S. Bell, University of Connecticut; Zachary K. Collier, University of Connecticut; Verónica Nelly Vélez, Western Washington University; Donna Y. Ford, The Ohio State University; David J. Connor, Hunter College - CUNY*

Between Rhetoric and Reality: MTSS and the Systemic Contradictions of Educational Equity. *Jane Y. Jeong, University of Texas at Austin; Catherine Kramarczuk Voulgarides, Hunter College - CUNY*

A Disability Justice Vision of Inclusive Education for Students with Complex Disabilities: Advancing Interdependent Ecologies. *Tamara Handy, Teachers College, Columbia University; Santasha Dhoot, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Reframing Global Articulations of Inclusive Education: A Decolonial Epistemic Justice Approach. *Tamara Handy, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Chair: *Nickie Coomer, Colorado College*

89.040. Building Reliable Tools: Psychometric Validation in Teaching and Learning Contexts. SIG-Survey Research in Education; Paper Session
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Echo Park; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Assessing Research-Led Teaching: Development and Validation of a Faculty Survey. *Rong Wang, Xi'an Jiaotong-Liverpool University; Xin Xu, Xi'an Jiaotong-Liverpool University*

Psychometric Evaluation of the Self-Directed Learning Instrument Among Rural Middle School Teachers. *Jui-Teng Li, Appalachian State University; Jason Snyder, Appalachian State University; Tyrel Winebarger, Appalachian State University; Rachel Shepherd, Appalachian State University; Corinne Smith, Appalachian State University; James Beeler, Appalachian State University; Erin K. West, Appalachian State University*

Teacher Workload Matters: A Validated Scale for Research and School Use. *Tim Pressley, Christopher Newport University; David T. Marshall, Auburn University; Heather Walter, George Mason University*

Validating a Literacy Practices Survey for Spanish-Speaking Early Grade Teachers. *Paola Andrea Guerrero-Rosada,*

University of California - Irvine; Siling Guo, University of California - Irvine; Caroline Chamberlain, University of California - Irvine

Validating Key Engagement Accelerators: A Confirmatory Factor Analysis of Student Engagement Constructs. *Davie Store, Kent ISD; Gavin Vance, Kent School District; Jennifer Rotach, Kent ISD; Daeja Marzette, Kent Intermediate School District*

Chair: *Jeffrey R. Albrecht, University of Michigan*

89.041. Conversing with AI: Fostering Student Inquiry and Socratic Dialogue. SIG-Technology as an Agent of Change in Teaching and Learning; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum B; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Asking Better Questions with AI: Student Inquiry, Critical Thinking, and the Role of Ask.Smile. *Trang Phan, California State University - Fresno; Meina Zhu, Wayne State University*

The Power of GenAI-enhanced Socratic Dialogue as a Scalable Learning Aid. *Jeonghyun Lee, Georgia Institute of Technology; Meryem Yilmaz Soylu, Georgia Institute of Technology; Jui-Tse Hung, Georgia Institute of Technology; Daniel Forsyth, Georgia Institute of Technology; Christopher Cui, University of California - San Diego*

From Bots to Mentors: Unveiling Dialogic Patterns in AI vs. Human Teacher Writing Instruction. *Siyuan Li, East China Normal University; Jing Leng, East China Normal University*

Chair: *Shuying Li, University of Nottingham*

Discussant: *Shuang Quan, Juniata College*

89.042. Aesthetics & Literacies across Educational Spaces. SIG-Writing and Literacies; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Atrium II; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Reading Genre Fiction Otherwise: Toward New Aesthetic Frameworks for Contemporary Literature Education. *Robert Jean LeBlanc, University of Lethbridge*

The Power of Interpretive Scale for Exploring Aesthetics in Social Life. *Scott Storm, University at Albany - SUNY*

Critical Aesthetic Inquiry in ELA Teacher Education. *Kelsey Leigh Stokes, Baylor University; T. Philip Nichols, Baylor University*

Reimagining Professional Development through Comic Conventions: Developing Teachers' Noticings Through Spaces of Aesthetic Education. *Karis Michelle Jones, Baylor University; Alecia Marie Magnifico, University of New Hampshire; Emily Ward Schindler, The Comic-Con Museum; Maggie Bryant, Baylor University*

Chair: *Scott Storm, University at Albany - SUNY*

Discussant: *Amy Stornaiuolo, University of Pennsylvania*

Division and SIG Roundtables

89.043. AERA Roundtable Session Sunday 7:45 am - Gold 1;
Roundtable Session

89.043-1. Roundtable Session 9: Student Learning and Development in College and Beyond (Table 1). Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

A New Future for College Engineering Students by Integrating Computational Modeling in Science Pedagogy. *Theresa A. Meyerott, California State University - Los Angeles; Jiwon Hwang, California State University - Los Angeles;*

Sungwook Hong, California State University - Bakersfield; Jeffrey Santner, California State University Los Angeles; Isha Patil, California State University Los Angeles

Factors Predicting Undergraduate Students' Academic Achievement and Later Life Outcomes. *Yen Vo, University of Iowa; Sonca Vo, University of Utah*

Generating Diverse Talent: Examining Who is Interested in Artificial Intelligence. *Chantra Nhien, University of California - Los Angeles; HyeJin Tina Yeo, University of California - Los Angeles; Catherine Jang, University of California - Los Angeles*

New Stories to Live By: Campus Green Spaces and Multispecies Meaning-Making. *Steve A. Tu, University of Toronto - OISE*

89.043-2. Roundtable 4 (Table 2). Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Are Post-secondary Students Prepared for Life after Graduation? Examining Characteristics and Correlates of Readiness Profiles. *Melvin Chan, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University*

Random Forest Modelling The Effects of Student Engagement on Academic and Career Persistence in Graduate Education. *Chaeyun Jeong, University of Georgia; Caleb Seung-hyun Han, University of Georgia; DaeSeok Chai, Texas A&M University*

The Impact of Early Achievements Under Pressure on Scientific Accomplishments. *Daozheng Li, Xiamen University; Sun Xiaoxiao, Peking University*

Chair: *Shuhan Ai, University of California - Los Angeles*

89.043-3. Roundtable 5 (Table 3). Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Uncovering Students' Website Evaluation Strategies: A Think-Aloud Analysis of Critical Online Reasoning Skills. *Andreas Maur, Johannes Gutenberg University of Mainz; Anika Kohmer, Johannes Gutenberg University of Mainz; Ann-Kathrin Kunz, Johannes Gutenberg University of Mainz; Maruschka Weber, Goethe University; Verena Klose, Goethe University; Yavuz Dinc, Ludwig Maximilian University of Munich; Verena Ruf, Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität München; Stefan Küchemann, Ludwig Maximilian University of Munich*

Are Reflective Papers Still a Valid Assessment? Examining Student Teachers' GenAI Use in Reflective Papers. *Tracy X. P. Zou, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Jodie X. J. Chen, Chinese University of Hong Kong*

Assessment Research in Higher Education: A Bibliometric Study on the Web of Science Database. *Meric Ozgeldi, Mersin University; Kenan Gökdag, University of Gaziantep; Utkun Aydin, University of Glasgow*

Chair: *Curtis G. Jefferson, University of Washington*

89.043-4. Centering Students and Student Leadership in Higher Education (Table 4). Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Borrowed Prestige, Forged Identities: Student Experience in the Sino-U.S. Cooperative University. *Liyan ZHU, Lingnan University*

Elevating University Students to Facilitate Institutional Change. *Susan P Farruggia, University of Illinois at Chicago; Jaeyun Han, University of Illinois at Chicago; Mikayla Strasser, University of Illinois at Chicago; Fructoso M Basaldua, University of Illinois at Chicago; Rachel Anna Yim, University of Illinois at Chicago; Carmen Lilley, University of Illinois at Chicago*

Futuring Student Learning: Repositioning Department Head Leadership in Canadian Higher Education. *Yu Zan, University of Saskatchewan; Paul Newton, University of Saskatchewan*

Intersectional Power and Institutional Change: Centering Student Leadership in Postsecondary Education. *Susannah C. Davis, University of Washington; Lia Wetzstein, University of Washington; Mayra Nuñez Martinez, University of California - Davis; Jordan Reed, University of Washington; Katherine M. Kovacich, University of Washington - Seattle*

Chair: *Amita Verma, University of South Carolina*

89.043-5. Career Integration, Readiness, and Support (Table 5). Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable

Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

An Agenda for Change: Faculty as Architects of Social and Economic Mobility through Career Integration. *Megan Brock, University of Georgia*

Career-Readiness: Requiring a Master's Research Project Experience. *Lois Calian Trautvetter, Northwestern University; Christopher Neary, Northwestern University*

From Policy to Practice: Institutional Mediation of Graduate Employment Support in Hong Kong and Shanghai. *Yichu Han, Hong Kong Metropolitan University; Jiangye Zhu, Lancaster University*

Chair: *Debalina Maitra, Kennesaw State University*

89.043-6. Beyond Tools and Tasks: Reimagining STEM Teaching Through Technology, Equity, and Teacher Insight (Table 6). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Beyond the Tool: Examining K-8 Science Teachers' Planning and Implementation of Technology Through the PICRAT Framework. *Adjoa Mensah, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Tina Vo, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Un Hyeok Ko, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*

Exploring Future Teachers' CT Learning with Scratch and Their Attitudes Toward Teaching with Similar Tools. *Whitney E. Wall Bortz, Fresno Pacific University; Tianying Feng, University of California - Los Angeles; Gregory K.W.K. Chung, University of California - Los Angeles*

It's More Than Just Numbers: Mathematics Task Adaptations for Cultural Relevance. *Kelly Dollarhide, University of Georgia; Susan Ophelia Cannon, University of Georgia*
Understanding Teacher Perspectives on Student Executive Function Skills for Mathematics Teaching & Learning. *Marisol Kevelson, Educational Testing Service; Caitlin Tenison, ETS; Jamie N. Mikeska, Educational Testing Service; Megan E Brunner, AERDF / EF+Math; Gabriela Rivera, AERDF; Michelle Tiu, AERDF*

Chair: *Adjoa Mensah, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*

Discussant: *Lisa D. Clark, Queens College - CUNY*

89.043-7. Charting New Pathways in Preservice Teacher Education (Table 7). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Comparison of Preservice Teachers' School-based and Video-based Lesson Analyses in an Undergraduate Educational Psychology Course. *Alpana Bhattacharya, Queens College -*

CUNY

Dialogic Spaces Created Through Ungraded Multimodal Portfolios: Inside, Undone and In-depth. *Amrit Kaur Cojocar, Simon Fraser University; Shaghayegh Bahrami, Simon Fraser University; Pooja Dharamshi, Simon Fraser University*

What Kind of Education resource Supply is Effective in Cultivating Normal College Students' Digital Literacy? *Li Liu, East China Normal University; Qinghao Li, East China Normal University; Lili Liu, East China Normal University*
Cultivating Expertise and Equity: The Impact of Practitioner Journals on Preservice Teacher Knowledge. *Allie J. Boquet, Louisiana State University; Renee Lastrapes, University of Houston - Clear Lake; Paul Mooney, Louisiana State University*

Chair: *Jean Baptiste Habarurema, University of Cincinnati*

89.043-8. Centering the Possibilities of AI in Teacher PD (Table 8). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Designing a Professional Development Workshop to Increase K12 Teachers' Artificial Intelligence (AI) Literacy and Self-Efficacy. *Virginia Byrne, Morgan State University; Valerie Riggs, Morgan State University; Wanda Roshell Debrewer, Morgan State University; Martha James Hassan, Morgan State University*

Innovating Professional Development: Co-Designing an AI Playground with Teachers, Developers, and District Leaders. *Samaa Haniya, Pepperdine University; Reyna G. Garcia-Ramos, Pepperdine University*

My Partner in Equity: AI-Mediated Scaffolding for Justice-Centered Leadership Through Dialogic Reflection. *Raketa Ouedraogo-Thomas, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Hannah Mesouani, University of San Diego*

Teachers' Professional Engagement with Literacy, Inquiry, Social Justice, and AI Technology in K-8 Classrooms. *Razak Kwame Dwomoh, Northern Illinois University; Eric R. Junco, Northern Illinois University; Cansu Tatar, Northern Illinois University; Hyoju Ahn, Northern Illinois University*

Thematic Analysis to Explore Teachers' Expectations on Professional Development Programs for Artificial Intelligence. *Juan Li, The Education University of Hong Kong; Lingyun Huang, The Education University of Hong Kong; Lan Yang, Education University of Hong Kong*

Chair: *Deborah D. Dailey, University of Central Arkansas*

89.044. AERA Roundtable Session Sunday 7:45 am - Gold 2; Roundtable Session

89.044-1. Decolonizing and Redefining Preparation: Global Policy Perspectives on Educator Development (Table 1).

Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Decolonising teacher education through integrating Education for Sustainable Development into the Namibian Social Studies Curriculum. *Eveline Omagano Anyolo, University of Namibia*

Shaping Policy: Stakeholder Perceptions of National Teacher Education Reforms in Norway. *Geoff Carlisle, Deans for Impact (DFI); Inga Staal Jensen, University of Oslo, Norway*

Unforgetting Policy: Reexamining the Histories and Futures of Principal Preparation Programs in the US. *Nahed Abdelrahman, The University of Southern Mississippi; Beverly J. Irby, Texas A&M University; Rafael Lara-Alecio, Texas A&M University*

What Makes Policy Work? Exploring institutional logics of action and policy sensemaking in Taiwan's Teaching Excellence Project. *MING-FENG LIU, Fu Jen Catholic University; Ya-Fei Yang, Center for Teacher Education, NTU*

Tutor-to-Teacher Pipeline: The Effect of Working as a Tutor on Interest in Teaching. *Jilli Jung, Stanford University; Carly D. Robinson, Stanford University; Susanna Loeb, Stanford University*

Chair: *Beverly J. Irby, Texas A&M University*

89.044-2. Holding On: Teacher Retention Amid Stress and Strain (Table 2). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

From Newcomers to Veterans: Uncovering Burnout Profiles and Influential Factors in Early- and Mid-Career Teachers. *Sohee Kim, University of South Alabama; Seoyeon Park, University of Nevada, Las Vegas*

How Resilience Contributes to Quality Retention: Narratives of Teachers Who Stay. *Christopher W. Day, University of Nottingham*

Why Do Unhappy Teachers Stay? A Qualitative Analysis of What Keeps Unhappy Teachers from Leaving. *Sophie Gullett, The New Teacher Project; Nancy L. Leech, University of Colorado - Denver; Carolyn A. Haug, Colorado Department of Education; Marisha Lamont-Manfre, University of Colorado - Boulder*

Why We Are Staying in the Profession: Counternarratives of Hope and Healing as Educators. *Molly Siebert, Hamline University*

Chair: *Molly Siebert, Hamline University*

89.044-3. Curricular Perspectives in Music Teacher Education (Table 3). SIG-Music Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

From Coursework to Classroom: Preservice Music Teachers' Application of Equity-Centered Classroom Management in Practicum Settings. *Daniel Taylor, Vanderbilt University*

How Music Education Students Use Pre-Performance Rituals to Manage Pressure and Anxiety. *Oksana Komarenko, Ball State University*

Meritocracy and the Shifting Boundaries Between Popular and Classical Music in Mainland Chinese Music Education. *Chenyu Li, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Never Ask Permission: Using Beyoncé's Music as Protest to Challenge Genre in the Music Classroom. *Bri'Ann Wright, California State University - Fullerton; Christian Michael Folk, University of Texas at Austin*

The Shock of Theory: Graduate Music Education Students Encounter Curriculum Thought and Reimagine Practice. *Cathy L. Benedict, Teachers College, Columbia University; Patrick Schmidt, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Chair: *Caroline Pearsall, Teachers College, Columbia University*

89.044-4. Addressing Challenges in Students' Learning of Mathematics (Table 4). SIG-Research in Mathematics Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

"A willingness to adapt": Special Education Elementary Candidates Making Sense of Inquiry Mathematics. *Rosa Chávez, California State University - Fresno; Faith Kwon, Stanford University*

Bridging Math Wars: Using GenAI and Metacognition to Design Mathematics Instruction for Students with Disabilities. *Ling Zhang, University of Wyoming; Tiffany Hunt, University of Wyoming; Miriam M. Sanders, University of Wyoming; Candace Joswick, University of Texas - Arlington*

Can Chess Improve Math Skills? Results from a Title I School-Based Randomized Controlled Trial. *Susanne DeFalco Harnett, Metis Associates, Inc.; Jenny D. Ingber, Chess in the Schools; Dawn Boyer, Metis Associates, Inc.*

Exploring a Framework for Mixed-Ability Mathematics Classrooms: An Adapted Differentiated Instruction Model. *Olivia Lu, University of Toronto; Sofia Ferreyro Mazieres, Wilfrid Laurier University; Douglas E. McDougall, University of Toronto - OISE*

The Impact of Model-based Problem Solving empowered by Problem Posing on At-Risk Students' Mathematics Performance. *Yan Ping Xin, Purdue University; Yichen Wang, Purdue University; Busra Yilmaz Yenioglu, Purdue University; Lejia (Morgan) Yu, Purdue University; Hannah Yanhua Zong, Purdue University*

Chair: *Nicole Fletcher, Fairfield University*

89.044-5. Addressing Identity Development in Mathematics Classrooms: Are We Helping or Hurting Our Students? (Table 5).

SIG-Research in Mathematics Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Beyond Stereotypes: Uncovering Symbolic Exclusion in School Mathematical Discourse. *Olimpia Gomez, Autonomous University of Yucatan*

How Self-Concept, Self-Efficacy, and Grit Contribute to Gender Differences in Middle School Mathematics Learning. *Yonghong Jade Xu, University of Memphis; Qiang Andy Cheng, University of Mississippi; Yu Wu, University of Memphis*

Influence of Teacher Care on Black Girls' Math Identity Development. *Angelica N. Robinson, San Diego State University; Brittany L. Marshall, San Diego State University*

Investigating Secondary School Students' Mathematical Well-Being and Its Relationship with their STEM Career Interests. *Qiaoping Zhang, University of Hong Kong; Lin Dan, The Education University of Hong Kong; Haomin FANG, The Education University of Hong Kong*

Unforgetting Critical Events in Mathematics Identity Development: A Multi-Institutional Narrative Analysis of Math Autobiographies. *Ethan P. Smith, Washington State University - Tri-Cities; Robyn K. Pinilla, University of Texas - El Paso; Ashley N. Schmidt, University of Wisconsin - Milwaukee; Sean P. Freeland, West Virginia University; Candice Hamilton, Texas State University; Brittney M. Ellis, Texas State University*

Chair: *Jennifer L. Ruef, University of Oregon*

89.044-6. Constructing New Understandings of Learning in Mathematics and Science Education (Table 6).

SIG-Socio-Political Issues in Mathematics and Science Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

"Fun" as a Social Practice: Reframing Learning Through the Eyes of Multilingual Students. *resmiye elifuzun, University of Massachusetts - Dartmouth; Shakhnoza Kayumova, University of Massachusetts - Dartmouth*

Held Between Two Fingers: Resisting Nature-Culture Divides in an Informal Science Learning Space. *Olivia Ortiz, New York University*

An Optimal Grip on Mathematics: An Embodied Critical Inquiry into Problem-Solving. *Gabriela M. Hernandez, San Diego State University; Christian Kronsted, Merrimack College*

A Proposal for Political Knowledge for Teaching Inclusive Mathematics; Theoretical Grounding. *Alexis Padilla,*

Independent Scholar; Paulo Tan, University of California - Santa Cruz; Rachel Lambert, University of California - Santa Barbara

Tensions in teaching mathematics through sociopolitical issues. *Mahati Kopparla, University of Pittsburgh*
Chair: *Ufomanefe Shola Kayode, Texas Tech University*

89.044-7. Global Practices and Insights on Disability (Table 7).

SIG-Special and Inclusive Education Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

South Korean Educators' Knowledge, Values, and Views on Inclusive Practices for Neurodevelopmental Disabilities. *Vania DaEun Jung, Denison University; Xiaoning Wang, Denison University*

Examining Relational Inclusivity for Newcomer Refugee Students Through an After-School Enrichment Program. *Christoforos Mamas, University of California - San Diego; Shana R. Cohen, University of California - San Diego; Bailey Choi-Vanos, University of California - San Diego; Caren Holtzman, University of California - San Diego*

Inclusive Voices in Action: Disability Advocacy through Educational Podcast in Mozambique. *Vanessa Sissi Lazaro Macamo-Santana, University of Arizona*

Are Chilean Schools Normalizing Punitive Disciplinary Practices? Evidence from Students and Parents. *Verónica López, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Valparaíso; Claudio Allende, Universidad de Chile; Juan Pablo Valenzuela, Universidad de Chile; Sebastián Ortiz, Universidad de Playa Ancha*

The prevalence and nature of dehumanization of students with special educational needs in Hong Kong. *Kuen Fung Kenneth Sin, The Education University of Hong Kong; Cheng Li, the Education University of Hong Kong; Tianfang Frank Ye, Hong Kong Polytechnic University; Lan Yang, Education University of Hong Kong; Fengzhan Gao, Education University of Hong Kong*

Chair: *Ilene Ivins, Alder Graduate School of Education*

89.044-8. Innovative Approaches to Mathematics Instruction for Students with Disabilities (Table 8).

SIG-Special and Inclusive Education Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Examining a Virtual Number Line Intervention to Teach Fractions to Children With Mathematics Difficulties. *Rajiv Satsangi, George Mason University; Soyoun Park, University of Central Florida*

A Case Study of Specially Designed Instruction for Middle School Math Students in Special Education. *David Johnston, Texas Tech University; Jeong-Hee Kim, Texas Tech*

University; Randi Wold-Brennon, Texas Tech University; Zoraya Davidson, Texas Tech Alumni; Aileen Narido Hermes, Texas Tech University

Exploring Problem-Solving Characteristics and Error Patterns in Fraction Word Problems Among Students with MLD. Lexi Hwang, California State University - Los Angeles; Kyle Chasen Hay, University of California - Los Angeles; Sarah R. Powell, University of Texas at Austin

89.044-9. Graduate Education Reimagined (Table 9). SIG-Graduate and Postdoctoral Education across the Disciplines; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Café of Control: A Graduate Student Persistence Digital Ethnography. Yvenord Mergilles, Florida International University
Curriculum Innovation in STEM Master's Degree Programs: A Systematic Literature Review. Karri A. Holley, University of Alabama; Khandakar Kamrul Hasan, University of Alabama
Doctoral Student Support Networks: Acknowledging Community. Karley Riffe, University of Cincinnati; Samantha Carroll, University of Cincinnati
From Struggle to Strategy: What Student Voices Reveal About Growth and Academic Thriving. Watcharasak Sudla, Chulalongkorn University; Laphatphitcha Surawatakul, Chulalongkorn University; Suthisak Salika, Chulalongkorn University

89.045. AERA Roundtable Session Sunday 7:45 am - Gold 3; Roundtable Session

89.045-1. Affect, Embodiment, and Art in Education (Table 1). SIG-Critical Posthuman and Postfoundational Studies in Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Affective Capacities of ASMRtistry for Qualitative Inquiry. Erin Bailey, Reading Is Fundamental
(Art)icu(late) multiself narratives: An autoethnography of (be)coming. Arisandy Johnson, Arizona State University
Becoming unproductive sensemakers. Kathryn M. Bateman, Pennsylvania State University - Harrisburg; Erin Bailey, Reading Is Fundamental; Natalie Purves, Deakin University; Kathleen Pleasants, University of Melbourne; Maarten Klene, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam; Lisa Siegel, Southern Cross University; Jonathan Lynch, Ara Institute of Canterbury
Pretty Pictures, Deeper Meanings: Youth Art Education and Transformative Encounters with Expression. Jennifer Jervis, California State University East Bay
Topologies of Subjectivation: Epistemic, Temporal, and

Political Foldings of Migrant Becoming. William Zhou, The George Washington University

Chair: William Zhou, The George Washington University

89.045-2. Policy, Equity, and Critical Perspectives in Bilingual Education (Table 2). SIG-Bilingual Education Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Do They See the Connection? Teacher Perceptions of Trauma-Informed Practices for Emergent Bilingual Learners. Ofelia Castro Schepers, Purdue University; Kathryn S. Young, Metropolitan State University of Denver; Megan Brennan, Resilient Futures
Equity Futures from the Borderlands: Mixed-Methods Analysis of Speculative Design for Multilingual Learner Policy Compliance. Sumin Lim, Hunter College
From Allocation to Action: Bilingual Education Budget Use Across New Mexico Districts for ELL Boys. Jenna Doane, The University of New Mexico; Wajih Saqib, University of Texas at Austin
From Compliance to Liberatory Cariño: Unforgetting and Reimagining SEI Through the Practices of Multilingual Teachers. Vanessa Quintana Sarria, University of Massachusetts - Boston
Futuring Multilingual Classrooms: Critical Linguistic Landscapes for Justice-Oriented, Future-Facing Teacher Education. Miriam Jorge, University of Missouri - St. Louis; Dawn Thieman, University of Missouri - St. Louis; Doris Villarreal, Ohio University

89.045-3. Preparing and Supporting Bilingual Teachers (Table 3). SIG-Bilingual Education Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

All Teachers are Language Teachers: An Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis of Educators' Transformative Journey in Supporting Multilingual Learners. Emily Holtz, University of Tennessee; Taylor Weber, University of Tennessee; Stephanie Michelle Moody, Towson University
Arts-Based Pláticas: Reimagining education Research with Transnational Bilingual Latina Educators. Astrid Sierra, Metropolitan State University of Denver
Bilingual Teacher Education: A Systematic Literature Review. Roya Pashmforoosh, Texas A&M University; Amirpooya Dardashti, Texas A&M University; Yanbing Chen, Texas A&M University; Mohsen Bemani Mohammadabadi, Texas A&M University; Hessameddin Ghanbar, Islamic Azad University
Dialogical acompañamiento: Towards co-agentive coaching for biliteracy praxis. Mariana L. Sánchez, University of Maryland; Sandra Natalia Gutiérrez, University of

Maryland - University College; Melinda E. Martin-Beltran, University of Maryland

Dual Language Teacher Candidates' Reframing Language Ideologies Through Critical Reflection: A Path Toward Transformation? Patricia M. Ferreyra, Western Washington University

89.045-4. Action Research as an Intellectual, Professional, Pedagogical, and Methodological Tool for Pre-Service Teacher Empowerment and Continuous Growth (Table 4). SIG-Action Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Action Research as a Tool for Pre-service Teacher Empowerment: A Two-Cycle Study. Neslihan Gok Ayyildiz, Middle East Technical University; Pervin Oya Taneri, Middle East Technical University; Gonca Cinar Bent, Middle East Technical University

Cultural Awareness in Action: A Pen Pal Program as a Pedagogical Tool for Preservice Teachers. Catherine Boggs, Texas A&M University; DaJuana Chaney Fontenot, Texas A&M University; Quintina D. Ogletree, Texas A&M University

Exploring Social Emotional Learning in Action Research: Teacher Residents' Inquiries & Identities in Urban Contexts. Vi Trinh, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Amanda Winkelsas, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Halley A. Maza, University at Buffalo - SUNY

Using Action Research to Close the "Research Practice Gap". Kim Lebak, Stockton University

Chair: Neslihan Gok Ayyildiz, Middle East Technical University

89.045-5. Systems, Policy, and Educational Futures in Sport (Table 5). SIG-Research Focus on Education and Sport; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Education's Kinetic Futures. Joshua Newman, Florida State University

How Are Maryland Athletes Managed for Successful Return to the Classroom? Edmund L. Mitzel, Notre Dame of Maryland University; Kathryn Doherty, Notre Dame of Maryland University; Angela L. Snyder, Notre Dame of Maryland University

School-Based Physical Activity Interventions among Children and Adolescents with Special Educational Needs and Disabilities: A Meta-Analysis. Jinghao SUI, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Cindy HP Sit, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Yijian Yang, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Jie FENG, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Ruiyuan Tao, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Jingsi WEN, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Chang Liu,

Tsinghua University

Determinants of Sports-Related Bachelor's Degrees at Power Five Institutions: Evidence of Prestige? Molly P. Harry, University of Florida

Chair: Maggie Mnayer, Central Michigan University

89.045-6. Exploring Literacy Self-Efficacy: From Student Motivation to Teacher Beliefs (Table 6). Division C - Learning and Instruction; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Bridging Confidence and Practice: Examining Teacher Self-Efficacy in Science of Reading Implementation Across Diverse Learners. Xinyan Fu, North Carolina State University; Jackie E. Relyea, North Carolina State University; Marie Himes, North Carolina State University; Dennis S. Davis, North Carolina State University; Jill F. Grifenhagen, North Carolina State University

GenAI-Assisted Growth-Oriented Feedback: Enhancing Students' Growth Mindset, Self-Efficacy and Performance in L2 Writing. Yi Guan, Hong Kong Polytechnic University; Xinhua Zhu, Hong Kong Polytechnic University; Yuan Yao, Hong Kong Polytechnic University; Longhai Xiao, Zhejiang University; Siyu Zhu, The Hong Kong Polytechnic University; Qinze Zhang, University of Manchester

Mapping the Structure of Literacy Self-Efficacy: Multidimensional and Correlated Constructs in Reading and Writing. Yucheng Cao, Middle Tennessee State University; Tien Ping Hsiang, University of Macau; Steve Graham, Arizona State University; Changchun Lin, Chongqing Normal University

Reading by Ear or Eye: Examining Comprehension, Self-Efficacy, and Reading Habits Across Audio and Print. Kayla King, San Francisco State University; Anisha Singh, San Francisco State University

The Nonlinear Relationship Between ICT Self-Efficacy and English Reading Achievement: An Island Ridge Curve Perspective. Qianwen Ge, Shanghai International Studies University; Yuyang Cai, Shanghai International Studies University

89.045-7. Exploring the Impact of AI and Technology on Literacy Instruction (Table 7). Division C - Learning and Instruction; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Analyzing Language Skills in Persuasive Writing and AI-Generated Feedback Using Factor Analysis Methods. Heqiao Wang, Old Dominion University

Building AI Teacher Competency: Framework Development and Evaluation Through Design-Based Research. Xinyan Zhou, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; SHUHENG

SHI, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Thomas K.F. Chiu, The Chinese University of Hong Kong

Evaluation of GPT-generated Readability Scores. Haiying Li, University of Pennsylvania; Xiner Liu, University of Pennsylvania; Fanshuo Cheng, University of Iowa; Zhiqiang Cai, The University of Memphis; Arthur C. Graesser, University of Memphis

Unpacking GAI's impacts on doctoral students' metacognitive experiences in summary writing: A mixed methods approach. Min Zou, Beijing Institute of Technology; Huiqing Quan, Beijing Institute of Technology; Liang Huang, Southeast University

Unpacking Online Feedback Uptake: How Students Use Instructor, Peer, and AI-Generated Feedback for Writing Revisions. Albert W. Li, University of California - Irvine; Penelope Collins, University of California - Irvine

89.045-8. Writing Development and Assessment Practices across Literacy Contexts (Table 8). Division C - Learning and Instruction; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Impact of Multi-source Feedback on EFL Learners' Engagement and Writing Performance in Chinese Classrooms. Lixia Li, East China Normal University; Jia Li, East China Normal University

Student-Generated Questioning as a Formative Approach to Writing Assessment. Angelie Ignacio, University of Toronto - OISE; Hajung Kim, University of Toronto - OISE; Han Lai, University of Toronto; Eunice Eunhee Jang, University of Toronto - OISE

The Stability of Beginning Writers' Profiles in Response to Sentence-Writing Instruction. Man Jiang, University of Delaware; David Coker, University of Delaware; Kristen D. Ritchey, University of Delaware

"20 Quiet Seconds to Think": Positioning Pre-K Students as Writers through Collective Idea Generation. Erica Lee Payne, Vanderbilt University; Deborah Rowe, Vanderbilt University

Chair: Jan Lacina, Texas Christian University

89.045-9. International Perspectives on the Teaching and Learning of Mathematics (Table 9). Division C - Learning and Instruction; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Disrupting Eurocentric Narratives: A Comparative Analysis of High School Geometry Curricula in India, Singapore, and the United States. Kamal Chawla, University of Maine; Christina Areizaga Barbieri, University of Delaware; Srujana Acharya, University of Delaware

Understanding Math Literacy Gaps: A Cross-National Machine

Learning Study of Motivational Predictors. Yiran Lin, McGill University; LUYAO XU, McGill University; Nikki G. Lobczowski, McGill University; Maria Cutumisu, McGill University

What works where? Identifying Pedagogical Practices to Optimize Data Literacy Learning in Singapore and America. Fabian Barch, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Jaekyung Lee, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Ji-Won Son, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Young Sik Seo, University at Buffalo - SUNY

Chair: La Toya Caton, Teachers College, Columbia University

89.046. AERA Roundtable Session Sunday 7:45 am - Gold 4;
Roundtable Session

89.046-1. Behavior and Achievement Across Contexts: Analyzing the Complex Web of Influence Through Mixed Methods (Table 1). Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Groups in Flux: A Novel Mixed-Methods Approach for Linking Narrative Data to Quantitative Analysis. Camila Torres Rivera, Guttman Community College

How Does School or Family Influence Students' Academic Achievements Over Time and Across Areas? Shuang GAO, Beijing Normal University

Online Positive Parenting Program: A mix-methods RCT on Parenting and Child Outcomes. Shiqi Wang, Beijing Normal University; Minyi LI, Beijing Normal University; Ni ZHANG, University of Hawaii - Manoa; Xinyu Wang, Beijing Normal University

Teachers' Behavior in building Agents: Based on Hierarchical Clustering and Thematic Analysis. Haiyang Xin, COCOROBO Limited; Yahui Yu, COCOROBO Limited; Shuang Li, University of Hong Kong; Qiannan Niu, COCOROBO Limited; Lei Gao, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Ching Sing Chai, Chinese University of Hong Kong

Chair: Kayla S. Burt, Massachusetts Institute of Technology

89.046-2. VR and Haptic Learning Experiences (Table 2). SIG-Advanced Technologies for Learning; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Blind and Visually Impaired Learners' Spatial Explorations and Imaginations with Haptic Technologies in STEM Education Co-Design. Sofia Tancredi, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Colton Doherty, Saint Louis University; Jennifer Tennison, Saint Louis University; Brett Fiedler, University of Colorado - Boulder; Jenna Gorlewicz, Saint Louis University; Dor Abrahamson, University of California -

Berkeley

Can We Trust AI as a Score Rater? A Preliminary Study on the Reliability and Validity of a GenAI Model's Assessment of Learning Performance Data. *Hao He, Emporia State University; Xinhao Xu, University of Missouri; Jhon Bueno-Vesga, Pennsylvania State University; Yupei Duan, University of Missouri; Shangman Li, University of Missouri; Yuanyuan Gu, University of Missouri; Sue Yun Fowler, University of Missouri; Hillary L. Claunch, University of Missouri; Jason Snyder, University of Missouri*

Case Study: User Experiences of a Multidisciplinary Team in a Virtual Production Studio Process. *Aino Ehrukainen, University of Lapland; Heli Ruokamo, University of Lapland*

Unpacking In-VR Learning Dynamics for Heat Stress Training: A Microgenetic and Sequential Behavior Analysis. *Idowu David Awoyemi, University of Alabama; Jewoong Moon, University of Alabama; Stephen Emmanuel Abu, University of Alabama; Raissa Marchiori, Florida Gulf Coast University; Siyuan Song, Arizona State University*

Virtual Reality-Based Cognitive Training for Older Adults: Meta-Analytic Insights Across Health Status, Interactivity, and Region. *Jing-I Wu, National Tsing Hua University*

Chair: *Soobin Jeon, University of Michigan*

89.046-3. Cultivating Connection: How Supportive Environments Promote Whole-Child Development (Table 3). Division H - Research, Evaluation and Assessment in Schools; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

The Hidden Costs of Absenteeism: Uncovering Associations with School Grades and Social and Emotional Wellbeing. *Pablo Luis Vivas Corrales, University of Minnesota; Michael C. Rodriguez, University of Minnesota; Julio Caesar, Bloomington Public Schools*

More Than Academics: How Student Support Services Shape School Attitudes. *Xiaohan Qian, Boston College; Yan Leigh, Boston College; Eric Dearing, Boston College; Mary Elizabeth Walsh, Boston College*

The Remarkable Longitudinal Consistency of Associations between Social & Emotional Wellbeing and Other Education Outcomes. *Michael C. Rodriguez, University of Minnesota; Tai Tri Do, University of Minnesota*

We Need a Village: School Connectedness Empowers Students to Move Beyond Bystanding Under an Anti-Bullying Climate. *Anqi Peng, Arizona State University; Sabina Low, Arizona State University*

Chair: *Almut K. Zieher, Yale University*

89.046-4. Arts based educational research and poetry (Table 4). SIG-Arts-Based Educational Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;

7:45-9:15am

Participants:

A Poetic Analysis of Youth's Critical Literacies as a Way of Being In and Beyond the Classroom. *Aimee Hendrix-Soto, Texas Woman's University*

Poetry as Experience: A Narrative Inquiry of Undergraduate Southwest Asian and North African (SWANA) Student Experiences in Texas. *Zianab Bayanzay, University of Houston*

"Poetry in Parks": Reading and Writing Poetry to Expand Humanizing Pedagogies, Environmental Consciousness, and Well-Being. *Alecia D. Beymer, University of Cincinnati; Mary Neville, Wayne State University*

Discussants: *Khalilah Odessa Ali, Spelman College; Patience Amadu, University of Colorado - Colorado Springs*

89.046-5. Title Written by AI? Make It Make Sense: Artificial Intelligence and Student Learning (Table 5). SIG-Data-Driven Decision Making in Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Thinking Critically Consciously with Generative Artificial Intelligence: Supporting Teacher Candidates' Data Literacy. *Derek R Riddle, California State University - Stanislaus; Paula Cristina Azevedo, Marymount University; Jori S. Beck, College of William & Mary; Catharyn Crane Shelton, Northern Arizona University; Jamie Colwell, Old Dominion University*

Faculty perspectives on AI visualizations of student data: Supporting pedagogy and sensemaking. *Priya Sharma, Pennsylvania State University; Mahir Akgun, Pennsylvania State University*

Governance, Privacy, and Integrity: A Comparative Analysis of Generative AI Platform Policies in K-12 Education. *Xianghui Meng, Columbia University; Shiyang Zhang, University of Pennsylvania*

Chair: *Kara Lasater, University of Arkansas at Fayetteville*

89.046-6. Cognitive Processes, Human-Technology Interaction, and Learning Analytics (Table 6). SIG-Technology, Instruction, Cognition & Learning; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Decoding Human and AI Persuasion in National College Debate Through Aristotle's Rhetorical Principles. *Mengqian Wu, McGill University; Jiayi Zhang, University of Pennsylvania; Raymond Zhang*

Exploring Cognitive Functions of Multiple-Choice Test-Takers: Visual Attention Related to Test Familiarity. *Elfa Nur Iftitah, University of Florida; Do Hyong Koh, University of Florida; Nancy Adams, University of Florida*

On the Trust Towards LLMs and Peers as Debate Partners: An Experiment. *Livia Kuklick, Humboldt University - Berlin; Elisabeth Mayweg, Humboldt University - Berlin; Lars Höft, DIPF | Leibniz Institute for Research and Information in Education*

The impact of virtual reality on skills acquisition, retention, and transfer: A systematic review. *Yuchun Zhong, Education University of Hong Kong; Kai Guo, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Lingran Xu, University of Sydney; Luke K. Fryer, University of Hong Kong*

Unlocking the Black Box: Use Bayesian Knowledge Tracing to Evaluate Perceptual Scaffolding in Math Intervention. *Puyuan Zhang, Worcester Polytechnic Institute; Siddhartha Pradhan, Worcester Polytechnic Institute; Erin R Ottmar, Worcester Polytechnic Institute*

Chair: *Deborah Moyaki, University of Georgia*

89.046-7. Dismantling educational and socio-cultural borders: Bilingualism is here to stay! (Table 7). SIG-Bilingual Education Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Formas con Voz: Storytelling as a Window Into Preschoolers' Geometric Reasoning. *Dafne Zanelli, Purdue University; Brenda Sarmiento-Quezada, Purdue University; Laura Bofferding, Purdue University; Yi Zhu, Purdue University*

From Monolingual Habits to Multilingual Horizons: A Middle-School Science Teacher's Translanguaging Journey in Two years. *Zhenjie Hou, University of Houston; Jie Zhang, University of Houston; Sissy S. Wong, University of Houston; Elisa M. Holcomb, University of Houston; Hien Thi Tran, University of Houston; Araceli Enriquez-Andrade, University of Houston*

Implementing Pedagogical Translanguaging in Multilingual Science Classrooms: Shifts, Affordances and Challenges. *Iftekhar Chowdhury, University of Houston; Jie Zhang, University of Houston; Sissy S. Wong, University of Houston*

89.047. AERA Roundtable Sunday 7:45 am; Roundtable Session

89.047-1. Developing and Supporting Teacher Leadership Roles (Table 1). Division A - Administration; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

(Re)Defining Teacher Leadership: Insights from the History of Black Teachers in the Segregated South. *Miyoshi Juergensen, University of Alabama - Birmingham*

Unpacking the Roles of Teacher Leaders: Perceptions of In-Service Teachers and Building-Level Leaders. *James Coaxum, Rowan University; Margaret Thornton, Rowan*

University; Joanne Connor, Rowan University; Gaëtane Jean-Marie, Rowan University; Matthew J. Stier, University of Iowa; Magdalena Martinez, Rowan University; JoAnn B. Manning, Rowan University

The Professional Development of Teacher Leaders in North Carolina's Advanced Teaching Roles Program. *Tamara V. Young, North Carolina State University; Sarah Byrne Bausell, North Carolina State University; Emily Plunkett Thrasher, North Carolina State University; Lam D. Pham, North Carolina State University; Jodie Roberson, North Carolina State University; Amber Lauren Moore, North Carolina State University; Shaun B. Kellogg, North Carolina State University; Thomas Mattos, North Carolina State University*

Rethinking Teacher Leadership: A Critical Cross-National Analysis of Eight Frameworks from Global North. *Fangju Jiao, Hokkaido University*

Unleashing as Unforgetting: Computer Science Teacher Relational Networks for Systemic Transformation. *Joanna Goode, University of Oregon; Adrienne Pinsoneault, University of Oregon; Casey Emmanuel Tiemann, University of Oregon; Jill Hubbard, Oregon State University - Cascades*

89.047-2. Digital Transformation and Educational Leadership (Table 2). Division A - Administration; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Transformative Leadership in Education: Unforgetting Histories to Foster AI-Enhanced, Culturally Responsive Learning for Sustainable Equity. *Wei Zhang, Western Michigan University; Shuzhen Xie, Marquette University; Meredith L. Reinhart, Western Michigan University; Katherine Suender, Western Michigan University*

School Principals' Perspectives and Leadership Styles for Digital Transformation : A Q-Methodology Study. *peili yuan, 北京师范大学; xinshen chen, Beijing Normal*

University; 昱泽陈, Tsinghua University; Huan Song, Beijing Normal University; Xingzhou Wang, Beijing Normal University

AI Literacy for Educational Leaders: Imagining Futures in K-12 Policy and Practice. *Son T. H. Pham, Nha Viet Institute; Charles L. Lowery, Virginia Tech*

Chair: *Kathleen Scott, Pepperdine University*

89.047-3. Collective Wisdom, Networked Action: Rebuilding School-Community Relationships for Equitable Futures (Table 3). Division A - Administration; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

How do external networks of family, school, and community

impact student academic achievement? *Xinlei LV, Zhejiang University; Shutao Wang, Xiamen University; Kaiwen Zhao, Xiamen University*

Redistributing Power, Restoring Relationships: Innovations for School–Community Governance. *Mikah Dyer, Arizona State University; Tara Lynn Bartlett, Arizona State University*

California School Board Members and Their Motivations to Run for Political Office. *Akunna Faith Uka, University of Southern California; Mariana de França Steil, University of Southern California; Amanda Lauren Pickett, University of Delaware; Vandeka J. Rodgers, University of Delaware*

“This group helps me think, but we need systems that help us act”: Examining Educator Transformation, Equity, and Belonging in a District-Led Learning Community. *Sophia Rodriguez, New York University; Sofia Antonia Gomez-Doyle, New York University; Lisa Lopez Escobar, University of Maryland; Melissa Ortiz, New York University*

Chair: *Jose Eos Trinidad, University of California - Berkeley*

89.047-4. Critical Research on Policy and Mattering within the Social Context of Education (Table 4). Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Naming Colonial Histories, Connecting through Kuwentuhan: The Formation of a Critical FilAm Research Group. *Erin Manalo-Pedro, University of California - Los Angeles; Krystle Cobian, University of California - Los Angeles; Elaine Jessica Castillo Tamargo, California State University - Long Beach; Gabbie Aquino-Adriatico, California State University - Fullerton; Christine Abagat Liboon, University of California - Los Angeles; Dina C. Maramba, Claremont Graduate University*

The Sherrification of Education; How Educational Policy Expands The School-To-Prison Pipeline and How We Interrupt It. *Martin Urbach, Graduate Center - CUNY*

Using Recognition Theory to Explore the Narratives of System-Impacted Students Who Earned College Degrees. *Adrian H. Huerta, University of Southern California; Jessica Leila Carranza, University of Southern California; Jose Bermejo, University of Southern California; David Oscar Moore, University of Southern California*

Vamos A Platicar: Reflecting on the English Learner Experience as formerly labeled ELs. *Marisa Ruiz, University of California - Davis*

Chair: *Juana Maria Reyes, Lewis University*

89.047-5. Strengthening Latine Bilingual Teaching Pathways Through Inter-Institutional Partnerships: Lessons From a Federally Funded HSI Grant (Table 5). Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Culturally and Linguistically-Sustaining Pedagogies in Future Bilingual Teacher Professional Development: Successes in Countering Erasure. *Sera Jean Hernandez, San Diego State University; Javier Diego Jacinto, Our Lady's School*
Modeling Democratic Praxis For Future Latine Bilingual Teachers. *Monique Escobedo, San Diego State University*
Refining Teacher Education Pathways From Community College to the University. *Michael Wickert, Southwestern College*

Applying “Servingness” to Evaluating a Bilingual Teacher Education Partnership Pathway in Hispanic-Serving Institutions. *Saul I. Maldonado, San Diego State University; Alberto Heredia, WestEd*

Chair: *Monique Escobedo, San Diego State University*

Discussant: *Mariano Lozano-Soto, San Diego State University*

89.047-6. Toward a Decolonial Vision of Educational Research (Table 6). Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

STEM for Sustainability: "Look to the Source, Seek Knowledge, Care for the Earth". *Pauline W.U. Chinn, University of Hawai'i at Manoa; Stacy Potes, University of Hawai'i Mānoa*

Responding to the Truth and Reconciliation Commission Calls to Action through Relationships. *Danielle Lamb, University of British Columbia - Okanagan; Margaret A. Macintyre Latta, University of British Columbia - Okanagan; William A. Cohen, University of British Columbia - Okanagan*

Methodology of Being: Towards an Ontoepistemology of Intuition in Education Research. *Rose Ann Rico Eborada Gutierrez, University of Nevada - Reno; Carolyn Silva, University of Nevada - Reno*

Reviving Indigenous Knowledge to Transform Multicultural Educational Practices. *Cheng Chang, Binghamton University - SUNY*

Chair: *Emily A. Affolter, Prescott College*

89.047-7. Toward a Transnational Educational Research Agenda (Table 7). Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Double Missions of Belonging and Blending In: Autistic Students' Voices with Transcultural Backgrounds. *Guangqian Grace Lyu, Simon Fraser University*

“It is not only an iPad!” –Language and Identity in a Transnational Family. *Xiao Hu, University of Utah*

Polyphonic Engagement and Transnational Dialogism: A Child's Reading Response to Realistic Fiction. *Shazia*

Hamid, University of South Carolina, Columbia

Reimagining Social Capital: Hybrid Adolescent Networks in Digital and Physical Spaces. *Maria Vilas, Ramon Llull University; Jordi Riera, Ramon Llull University; Elena Carrillo Alvarez, Ramon Llull University*

Chair: *Yan Jiang, Stanford University*

89.047-8. Youth Identity Development and Social

Relationships (Table 8). SIG-Adolescence and Youth Development; Roundtable Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Agentic Social Play and Peer Relationships: Evidence from a Pandemic-Era Survey of Youth. *Menissah E. Bigsby, University of California - Los Angeles*

Civic engagement and persistence among Chinese teenagers: The mediating effect of peer relationships and growth mindset. *Qianyu Zhou, East China Normal University; Hong Zhang, East China Normal University; Hanwei Tang, East China Normal University; Peng Wenqi, East China Normal University*

Exploring Heterogeneous Effect of Friend's Academic Foundation on Adolescents' Academic Achievement. *Boyuan LIU, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Si Chen, The Chinese University of Hong Kong*

How Exposure to Racial and Ethnic Diversity in High School Shapes Civic Engagement Among Latinx Youth. *Brittney Marques, California State University - Dominguez Hills; Kara Kogachi, University of California - Los Angeles; Sandra Graham, University of California - Los Angeles*

Parental Companionship and Its Influence on Children's Academic Performance: Mediating the Role of Educational Expectations. *Chenrui Zhu, East China Normal University; Shiqing Liu, East China Normal University; Qian Nie, East China Normal University*

Chair: *Kelly Ann Peña, Rutgers University*

89.047-9. Practicing Improvement: Challenges and Opportunities to Facilitating Improvement (Table 9).

SIG-Improvement Science in Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

Facilitating Participatory Design: A Framework to Analyze Talk Moves and Roles. *Ha Nguyen, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Jennifer Pei, University of California - Irvine; Yemy Pham, University of California - Irvine; Sara Ludovise, Orange County Department of Education; Rossella Santagata, University of California - Irvine*

Story Work in the Humanizing of Educational Improvement. *Carlos Sandoval, Clemson University; Parker Morse Andreoli, Clemson University*

When Time Gets in the Way: Understanding Time-Related Challenges in Improvement Networks. *Angel Yee-lam Li, Carnegie Foundation for the Advancement of Teaching; Jennifer Zoltners Sherer, University of Pittsburgh; Anthony S. Bryk, Carnegie Foundation for the Advancement of Teaching*

Chair: *Heather M. Dulas, University of Houston*

Division and SIG Posters

89.048. AERA Poster Session Sunday 7:45 am; Poster Session

89.048-1. Associations Among Pre-Service Teachers' Prior Experiences, Self-Esteem, and Racial and Teaching Self-Efficacy. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Poster Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 7:45-9:15am

Poster:

1. Associations Among Pre-Service Teachers' Prior Experiences, Self-Esteem, and Racial and Teaching Self-Efficacy (Poster 1). *Hyun-Joo Jeon, University of Nevada - Reno; Brianna Barnes, University of Nevada - Reno; Ravyin Routsis, University of Nevada - Reno; Jillian Way, University of Nevada - Reno*

89.048-2. Teachers' Perspectives on the State of the Profession and its Future. Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Poster Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 7:45-9:15am

Poster:

2. Teachers' Perspectives on the State of the Profession and its Future (Poster 2). *Caitlin Ione Brecklin, University of North Dakota; Lena Batt, University of Kansas*

89.048-3. Disposition, Identity and Intention: Understanding Adult Learning and Educational Engagement. SIG-Adult Literacy and Adult Education; Poster Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 7:45-9:15am

Posters:

3. Dispositional and Socio-Environmental Drivers of Adult Learning: Evidence from Singapore's Public Sector (Poster 3). *Charmaine Tan, Agency for Science, Technology and Research; Walter Theseira, Singapore University of Social Sciences*
4. Exploring Immigrant Adult Literacies through AI: A Case Study using ChatGPT (Poster 4). *Jin Kyeong Jung, Texas Tech University*
5. Prior Knowledge and AI Engagement Intentions in Non-STEM Graduate Students (Poster 5). *Shenghua Zha,*

University of South Alabama; Yuming He, Suffolk University; Wu He, National Science Foundation

6. Profiling Middle-Aged Adults' PIAAC Competencies: Education and Work Effects in Korea and the U.S. (Poster 6). *Jiyoung Ha, Yonsei University; Woo-jeong Shim, Hannam University; Jeong-a Kim, Korean Educational Development Institute*
7. Searching for a Social Vaccine for Skill Loss: Analyses of 2nd Cycle PIAAC Data (Poster 7). *Frank Fernandez, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Huacong Liu, Shanghai Jiao Tong University*

89.048-4. Childhoods, Materials, and Critical Learning Encounters. SIG-Critical Perspectives on Early Childhood Education; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 7:45-9:15am

Posters:

8. From Silence to Story: Mapping Climate Justice and Relational Literacies in Early Childhood (Poster 8). *Jessica Ramos, University of Colorado - Denver; Lauren Fletcher, California State University - Stanislaus; Erica Holyoke, University of Colorado - Denver*
9. Reading Erasure: A Critical Discourse Analysis of Latino/x Male Representation in Children's Literature and Its Role in Early Childhood Education (Poster 9). *Ryan C. Miller, University of Texas at Austin*
10. Safe for Whom? A Multispecies Ethnography of Care and Danger in a Chinese Kindergarten (Poster 10). *Bonan Liu, University of Muenster*
11. Toward an Ethics of Care and Vulnerability: Refiguring More-Than-Human Presences in Preschoolers' Multispecies Encounters (Poster 11). *Luke Max Muscat, St. Luke's School*
12. Visual Pedagogy in Palestinian-Jewish Bilingual Kindergartens: Navigating Conflict and Critical Multiculturalism in Israel-Palestine (Poster 12). *Zohar Sitner, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev; Assaf Meshulam, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev*
13. What does it mean to be global citizens?: A critical content analysis of picturebooks (Poster 13). *Xiaoying Zhao, Illinois State University; Ling Hao, Illinois State University*
14. When Pens Speak: Rethinking Field and Material in A Posthumanist Educational Ethnography with Children (Poster 14). *Bonan Liu, University of Muenster; Ziwen Mei, University of British Columbia*
15. Folding the Margin: Rhythmic Doodling as Immanent Self-Regulation in A Confucian Mathematics Classroom (Poster 15). *Lin Chen*
16. Transitioning into day care – the potential of translanguaging for families and early childhood educators (Poster 16). *Franziska C. Vogt, St. Gallen University of Teacher Education*
17. A White Child with Autism Spectrum Disorder's Engagement with Stories of Slavery and Freedom (Poster 17). *Hyeonryang Lim, The University of Texas at Austin; John Wright, Pacific Lutheran University; Jennifer Keys Adair, The University of Texas at Austin*

89.048-5. Educating for Climate Literacy and Justice: Preparing Teachers, Students, Communities, and Institutions for Sustainable Futures. SIG-Environmental Education; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 7:45-9:15am

Posters:

18. Antecedents of AI-assisted environmental protection intentions: The perspectives of digital literacy, cognitive-moral factors, and environment (Poster 18). *Mingyue DU, Hunan University; XINGWEI WANG, Tsinghua University; Xiuyuan Yang, Tangling Trust School Singapore; Shihan Zhang, American Heritage School of Plantation; Xiaohong Zhou, Tsinghua University*
19. Bridging Theory and Practice: A University-Led Sustainability Hub Empowering Youth Through Experiential Environmental Education (Poster 19). *Shenghua Wu, University of South Alabama; Melike Dizbay-Onat, University of South Alabama; Kaushik Venkiteshwaran, University of South Alabama; Matthew Patterson, University of South Alabama; Lu Ding, University of South Alabama*
20. Defending green spaces and transforming urban peripheral communities: A Photovoice Study in San Juan de Lurigancho (Lima, Peru) (Poster 20). *Jennifer Ponce-Cori, University of Pittsburgh*
21. Environmental Attitudes Measurement Validity in TIMSS 2023: Cross-National Comparisons (Poster 21). *Christopher Irwin, Florida International University*
22. Family Background and Environmental Awareness: Evidence from TIMSS 2023 Among U.S. Eighth-Grade Students (Poster 22). *Renda Sun, Teachers College, Columbia University; Neil Potnis, Teachers College, Columbia University*
23. From Global Policy to Local Classrooms: The Hidden Dynamics of Environmental Education Worldwide (Poster 23). *Sukie Xiuqi Yang, University of Pennsylvania*
24. Green Schools, Sustainable Future: The Impact of Schools on Environmental Awareness in Morocco (Poster 24). *Jabrane Amaghous, Cadi Ayyad University*
25. How Students Express Environmental Values After Learning About Energy Flow in Natural and Built Environments (Poster 25). *Jessica Ann Justice, University of Missouri; Laura Zangori, University of Missouri; Laura Cole, Colorado State University*
26. Less Concerned and Not a Priority: Evidence from a Climate Literacy Assessment of Education Students (Poster 26). *Samantha A. Lindgren, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Aigul Rakisheva, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*
27. Preparing Sustainability-Literate Teachers: Outcomes of an

- Education Training Program (Poster 27). *Aigul Rakisheva, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Samantha A. Lindgren, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*
28. Psychology of Environmental Sustainability: Examining Intersections between Perceptions of Environmental Fear, Renewable Energy, and Levels of Education (Poster 28). *Ferhat Ozbay, Isparta University of Applied Sciences; Zafer Adiguzel, Sakarya University of Applied Sciences; Ibrahim Duyar, Arkansas State University*
29. Supporting Teachers in Making Decisions About Complex Problems: Redesigning Labs Through a Green Chemistry Lens (Poster 29). *Alexandra Collard, University of California - Berkeley; Anne Baranger, University of California - Berkeley; Marcia Linn, University of California - Berkeley*
30. Toward Equitable Futures in Environmental and Sustainability Education: A Scholarly Review of Social Studies Advocacy (Poster 30). *Yun Wen Chan, Texas State University; Theresa Alviar Martin, Kennesaw State University*

Chair: *Megan Ennes, University of Florida*

89.048-6. Equitable Participation and Discourse in Science Teaching and Learning. SIG-Science Teaching and Learning; Poster Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 7:45-9:15am

Posters:

31. Examining the Impact of an Out-of-School Program on Underrepresented Youths' STEM Identity and Belonging (Poster 31). *Xornam Apedoe, University of San Francisco; Katherine Nielsen, University of California - San Francisco*
32. Modeling & Dialogic Argumentation in an Urban High School Biology Classroom (Poster 32). *Katherine Michelle St. Clair Misar, SUNY - College at New Paltz*
33. On becoming a reformed physics teacher: A discourse analysis (Poster 33). *Marsha E. Simon, Valdosta State University; Justina Ogado, Baylor University; Dennis Sunal, University of Alabama; Cynthia S. Sunal, University of Alabama*
34. Partnerships Between Home and School: Parents Teaching Science in a Unique Hawai'i Charter School Program (Poster 34). *Randi Wold-Brennon, Texas Tech University; Jeong-Hee Kim, Texas Tech University; David Johnston, Texas Tech University; Zoraya Davidson, Texas Tech Alumni; Aileen Narido Hermes, Texas Tech University*
35. Reimagining Science Talk: Investigating Elementary Teachers' Discussion Practices During the Equitable Classroom Discussion Intervention (Poster 35). *Lin Yan, Arizona State University; Jeremy Bernier, Clemson University; Carla M. Firetto, Arizona State University*
36. Authentic Science Labs: Exploring Youth STEM Occupational Identity and Addressing Barriers (Poster 36). *Audrey Buzard, University of Pittsburgh; Dustin Dusing, University of Pittsburgh; Nathan Cho, University of Pittsburgh; Cassie F. Quigley, University of Pittsburgh; Abigail Matela, University of Pittsburgh; Colton Siakowski, University of Pittsburgh; Vaughn Cooper, University of Pittsburgh*
37. Demonstrations of STEM Identities in a Place Based Renewable Energy Afterschool Workshop (Poster 37). *Allison Antink-Meyer, University of Missouri - St. Louis; Jeritt Williams, Illinois State University; Matthew Aldeman, Illinois State University; Jin Jo, Illinois State University*
38. Social Resources Supporting Teachers' Design of Localized Curricula: Images of the Possible (Poster 38). *Monica Sircar, Stanford University*
39. Socioeconomic Status and Science Achievement: The Role of Views of Science (Poster 39). *Yu-Jou Joyce Chou, Pennsylvania State University; Brian R. Belland, Pennsylvania State University*
40. Supporting Student Motivation Through Community-Relevant Elementary Engineering Lessons (Poster 40). *Lauren Cabrera, University of Michigan - Dearborn; Jenna Gist, Purdue University; Julie Robinson, University of North Dakota; Min Jung Lee, University of North Dakota; Rebekah Hammack, Purdue University; Tugba Boz, University of North Dakota*
41. Toward Equitable Distributions of Authority in Science Classroom Collaborative Groupwork (Poster 41). *Etta C Pope, Northwestern University; Olga Vaskova, Northwestern University; Jason Buell, Northwestern University; Brian J. Reiser, Northwestern University*
42. What is the impact of giving students guidance on their infrequent ideas in an AI Dialog? (Poster 42). *Allison Bradford, University of California - Berkeley; Libby F. Gerard, University of California - Berkeley; Weiyang Li, University of California - Berkeley; Marcia Linn, University of California - Berkeley*

89.048-7. Belief Systems at Work: Mindset and Achievement Goal Research. SIG-Motivation in Education Cosponsored with Division C - Learning and Instruction; Poster Session Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 7:45-9:15am

Posters:

43. Adolescent Achievement Goal Development: Differential Time-Varying Effects of Perceived TARGET Dimensions in Classrooms (Poster 43). *Minhye Lee, Daegu National University of Education; Dajung Diane Shin, Kyungnam University*
44. Am I a Gatekeeper? An Exploration of Gatekeeper Beliefs in STEM Instructors (Poster 44). *Katherine M. Muenks, University of Texas at Austin; Taylor Payne, Rice University; Nathaniel Woznicki, New York University; Julie Sievers, University of Texas at Austin; Allison Zengilowski, Lehigh University; Afya C. Fredericks, University of the District of Columbia; Yiqiu Yan, University of Texas at*

Austin

45. Are Fixed and Growth Mindsets Opposite Ends of a Single Continuum? Examining the Mindset Dimensionality (Poster 45). *Dayeon Jeong, Korea University - Brain and Motivation Research Institute; Jimin Suh, Korea University - Brain and Motivation Research Institute; Pey-Yan Liou, Korea University; Mimi Bong, Korea University*
46. Beyond Beliefs: A Network Analysis of the Growth Mindset Meaning System in a Global Sample (Poster 46). *I Marie Joy Santillana Gallemet, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Yi Wang, Macau University of Science and Technology; Andrew J. Elliot, University of Rochester; Ronnel B. King, Chinese University of Hong Kong*
47. Income Inequality Weakens the Benefits of Mastery-Approach Goals in Academic Achievement (Poster 47). *Yikang Chen, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Ronnel B. King, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Andrew J. Elliot, University of Rochester*
48. Latent Profiles of Academic and Social Achievement Goals: Differences in Sociocognitive Conflict Regulation (Poster 48). *Jawon Min, Korea University; ByungYoon Lee, Sookmyung Women's University; You-kyung Lee, Sookmyung Women's University*
49. Longitudinal Changes in Preservice Elementary Math Teachers' Mindsets Across Three Courses (Poster 49). *Kahyun Lee, University of Houston; Allison Master, University of Houston; Carrie Cutler, University of Houston; Suppanut Sriutaisuk, Chulalongkorn University; Justin T. Burris, University of Houston*
50. Revisiting the "Multiple Goals" Perspective: Do People Find Mastery and Performance Goals Compatible? (Poster 50). *Corwin Senko, SUNY - College at New Paltz; Lucia Speranza, SUNY - New Paltz*
51. The Relationship Between Students' Growth and Fixed Mindsets: A Meta-Analysis (Poster 51). *Shengjie Lin, University of New Mexico; Yu-Yu Hsiao, University of New Mexico; Lindsey Jurgensen, University of New Mexico; Qing Wang, University of New Mexico; Katherine M. Muenks, University of Texas at Austin; Carlton J. Fong, Texas State University*
52. Understanding Growth Mindset Typologies at both Student and School Levels: A Multilevel Latent Profile Analysis (Poster 52). *Hebin LI, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Jiaping LI, Beijing Normal University; Morris Siu-Yung Jong, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Ronnel B. King, Chinese University of Hong Kong*

89.048-8. International Students and Academic Discourse.

Division G - Social Context of Education; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall -
Exhibit Hall A; 7:45-9:15am

Poster:

53. International Students' Academic Discourse Socialization and Identity Negotiation in U.S. from Global South

Perspective (Poster 53). *Zhixian Zhuang, University of Delaware; Christina M. Budde, University of Delaware*

89.049. Meet the Editors - Journal Talks Session 4. AERA

Sessions; Journal Talks

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
7:45-9:15am

Participants:

1. Asia Pacific Journal of Education (Table 1). *Dennis Kwek, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University; Hwei Ming Wong, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University; Katherine Shee, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University; Lorraine Renfeng Ow, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University*
2. International Journal of Qualitative Studies in Education (Table 2). *Cleveland Hayes, Indiana University - Indianapolis*
3. Journal of Language, Identity, and Education (Table 3). *Wayne E. Wright, Purdue University*
4. Journal of Research in Rural Education (Table 4). *Karen Eppley, Pennsylvania State University*
5. Journal of Urban Mathematics Education (Table 5). *Jamaal Young, Texas A&M University; Eboni N. Bango, Texas A&M University*
6. Mathematical Thinking and Learning (Table 6). *Heather Lynn Johnson, University of Colorado - Denver*
7. Middle School Journal (Table 7). *Lisa M Harrison, Ohio University; Kristie W. Smith, Kennesaw State University; Ellis Hurd, Illinois State University*
8. Research in Higher Education (Table 8). *Lauren Schudde, University of Texas at Austin; Lara Perez-Felkner, Florida State University*
9. State University of New York (SUNY) Journal of the Scholarship of Engagement (JoSE) (Table 9). *Jose Ortiz, SUNY Cortland*
10. The Interdisciplinary Journal of Problem-Based Learning (Table 10). *Krista D. Glazewski, North Carolina State University; Woei Hung, University of North Dakota; Xun Ge, University of North Texas; Kimberly B. Farnsworth, North Carolina State University; Parvej Ahmed, University of North Dakota*
11. The International Multilingual Research Journal (Table 11). *Jeff MacSwan, University of Maryland; Anna Mendoza, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Deborah K. Palmer, University of Colorado - Boulder; Luis E. Poza, San José State University; Bedrettin Yazan, University of Texas - San Antonio; Katharine Glanbock, University of Maryland*
12. Theory & Research in Social Education (Table 12). *Anne-Lise F. Halvorsen, Michigan State University*
13. Dual Language Research and Practice Journal (Table 13). *Beverly J. Irby, Texas A&M University; Nahed Abdelrahman, The University of Southern Mississippi; Rafael Lara-Alecio, Texas A&M University*

89.050. e-Lightning Ed-Talk Session 20 - Stage 1. AERA e-Lightning Ed-Talks; AERA Ed Talk
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Exhibit Hall A
- Stage 1; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

- Profiling Middle-Aged Adults' PIAAC Competencies: Education and Work Effects in Korea and the U.S. (Stage 1, 7:50 AM). *Jiyoung Ha, Yonsei University; Woo-jeong Shim, Hannam University; Jeong-a Kim, Korean Educational Development Institute*
- Dispositional and Socio-Environmental Drivers of Adult Learning: Evidence from Singapore's Public Sector (Stage 1, 7:59 AM). *Charmaine Tan, Agency for Science, Technology and Research; Walter Theseira, Singapore University of Social Sciences*
- A White Child with Autism Spectrum Disorder's Engagement with Stories of Slavery and Freedom (Stage 1, 8:08 AM). *Hyeonryang Lim, The University of Texas at Austin; John Wright, Pacific Lutheran University; Jennifer Keys Adair, The University of Texas at Austin*
- Reading Erasure: A Critical Discourse Analysis of Latino/x Male Representation in Children's Literature and Its Role in Early Childhood Education (Stage 1, 8:26 AM). *Ryan C. Miller, University of Texas at Austin*
- Toward an Ethics of Care and Vulnerability: Refiguring More-Than-Human Presences in Preschoolers' Multispecies Encounters (Stage 1, 8:35 AM). *Luke Max Muscat, St. Luke's School*
- Unraveling the Colonial Illusion of Representation: Material Agency for Relational Ethics in Early Childhood Art Inquiry (Stage 1, 8:44 AM). *Hyewon Oh, Growing Place Ocean Park Early Childhood Education Center*
- Teachers' Perspectives on the State of the Profession and its Future (Stage 1, 7:50 AM). *Caitlin Ione Brecklin, University of North Dakota; Lena Batt, University of Kansas*
- Chair: *Julie M. Slayton, University of Southern California*

89.051. e-Lightning Ed-Talk Session 20 - Stage 2. AERA e-Lightning Ed-Talks; AERA Ed Talk
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Exhibit Hall A
- Stage 2; 7:45-9:15am

Participants:

- From Silence to Story: Mapping Climate Justice and Relational Literacies in Early Childhood (Stage 2, 8:53 AM). *Jessica Ramos, University of Colorado - Denver; Lauren Fletcher, California State University - Stanislaus; Erica Holyoke, University of Colorado - Denver*
- Psychology of Environmental Sustainability: Examining Intersections between Perceptions of Environmental Fear, Renewable Energy, and Levels of Education (Stage 2, 7:59 AM). *Ferhat Ozbay, Isparta University of Applied Sciences; Zafer Adiguzel, Sakarya University of Applied Sciences; Ibrahim Duyar, Arkansas State University*

Antecedents of AI-assisted environmental protection intentions:

The perspectives of digital literacy, cognitive-moral factors, and environment (Stage 2, 8:17 AM). *Mingyue DU, Hunan University; XINGWEI WANG, Tsinghua University; Xiuyuan Yang, Tangling Trust School Singapore; Shihan Zhang, American Heritage School of Plantation; Xiaohong Zhou, Tsinghua University*

Are Fixed and Growth Mindsets Opposite Ends of a Single Continuum? Examining the Mindset Dimensionality (Stage 2, 8:26 AM). *Dayeon Jeong, Korea University - Brain and Motivation Research Institute; Jimin Suh, Korea University - Brain and Motivation Research Institute; Pey-Yan Liou, Korea University; Mimi Bong, Korea University*

Socioeconomic Status and Science Achievement: The Role of Views of Science (Stage 2, 8:35 AM). *Yu-Jou Joyce Chou, Pennsylvania State University; Brian R. Belland, Pennsylvania State University*

Authentic Science Labs: Exploring Youth STEM Occupational Identity and Addressing Barriers (Stage 2, 8:44 AM). *Audrey Buzard, University of Pittsburgh; Dustin Dusang, University of Pittsburgh; Nathan Cho, University of Pittsburgh; Cassie F. Quigley, University of Pittsburgh; Abigail Matela, University of Pittsburgh; Colton Siakowski, University of Pittsburgh; Vaughn Cooper, University of Pittsburgh*

Chair: *Rouhollah Aghasaleh, California State Polytechnic University - Humboldt*

Sunday, April 12th, 8:00 am

90.010. George Washington University Forum Democracy & Education - Session 3. Affiliated Groups; Panel Discussion
Westin Bonaventure, Level 2, Rodeo; 8:00am to 12:00pm

Sunday, April 12th, 8:15 am

AERA Sessions

91.010. AERA Business Meeting. AERA Sessions; Business Meeting
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 403B;
8:15-9:15am
Chairs: *Tabbye M. Chavous, American Educational Research Association; Maisha T. Winn, Stanford University; Jerome E. Morris, University of Missouri - St. Louis*

Sunday, April 12th, 9:45 am

Presidential Sessions

92.010. Understanding the Moment Across Multiple Marginalities: Navigating Attacks on Intersectional Educational Futures. AERA Presidential Session; Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 404AB;
9:45-11:15am

Chair: *Sharim Hannegan-Martinez, University of Michigan*
Presenters: *Nolan L. Cabrera, University of Arizona; John B. Diamond, Brown University; Harper B. Keenan, University of British Columbia; Qui Alexander, University of Toronto; Allyson Tintiangco-Cubales, San Francisco State University; Theresa Montano, California State University - Northridge*
Discussant: *Shamari Reid, New York University*

92.011. Unforgetting Deficit Depictions: Disrupting Education Systems of Injustice to Unlock the Hidden Geniuses. AERA Presidential Session; Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 406AB;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:
“We Want to be Seen, not Surveilled”: Black Students Telling Their Side of the Story. *Jaleel R. Howard, University of California - Riverside*
The Genius is Not Hidden—They just weren’t looking: Refusing erasure in the lives of Black foster youth. *Brianna Marche’ Harvey, California State University - Fullerton; Tyrone C. Howard, University of California - Los Angeles*
“I Fell Right into the Stereotype:” Carceral Figured Worlds and Latina Girls’ Identity Development. *Julissa O. Muñiz, University of California - Los Angeles; Armando Lizarraga, University of Texas at Austin*
Culturally Responsive Caring for Chinese American Students Post-Pandemic. *Lin Wu, Western Oregon University*
“The Genius Life of Students: Past and Present”. *Gholdy Muhammad, University of Chicago*
Uncovering Student Assets in Undergraduate University Courses. *Rich Milner, Vanderbilt University; John Nathaniel Singer, Texas A&M University*
Chair: *Tyrone C. Howard, University of California - Los Angeles*
Discussant: *Tyrone C. Howard, University of California - Los Angeles*

AERA Sessions

92.012. The Life and Legacy of Dr. Ernest D. Morrell: A Call to Embrace Our Collective Oaths. AERA Sessions; Invited Speaker Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 408A;
9:45-11:15am
Chairs: *Cati V. de los Rios, University of California - Berkeley;*

Jamila Lyiscott, University of Massachusetts - Amherst
Participants: *Nicole Mirra, University of California - Los Angeles; Kris D. Gutiérrez, University of California - Berkeley; Carol D. Lee, Northwestern University; Pedro A. Noguera, University of Southern California; Laurence Tan, University of California - Los Angeles; Van T. Lac, University of Illinois at Chicago; Antero Garcia, Stanford University; Yolanda Sealey-Ruiz, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Committee Sessions

92.013. Caregiving While Studying: Toward Just and Equitable Graduate Education. Graduate Student Council; Invited Speaker Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 402A;
9:45-11:15am
Chair: *Edith P. Middleton, Teachers College, Columbia University*
Panelists: *Cammie Justus-Smith, Virginia Commonwealth University; Xi Hong, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Micaha Dean Hughes, North Carolina State University; Abby C. Emerson, Touro University*

92.014. In the Spirit of Sankofa: Black Educational Thought in These Troubling Times. Committee on Scholars of Color in Education; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 301A;
9:45-11:15am
Participants:
Theories about Blackness in Education: Amplifying the Black Radical Tradition as a Path Toward Black Educational Futures. *Wintre Foxworth Johnson, University of Virginia; Samiha Rahman, California State University - Long Beach*
Critical Race Theory and the Legacy of Black Educational Thought. *Adrienne D. Dixson, Pennsylvania State University; Gloria J. Ladson-Billings, University of Wisconsin - Madison*
Reclaiming Communally Bonded Educators: A New, but Old Vision for the Field and Function of Black Educators. *Jerome E. Morris, University of Missouri - St. Louis; Luimil Negrón, University of Missouri - St. Louis*
Chairs: *Ronald E. Chennault, DePaul University; Derrick Alridge, University of Virginia*
Discussant: *Camika Royal, Morgan State University*

WERA Sessions

92.015. Navigating Education Research Worldwide in a Time Dismissive of Evidence. World Education Research Association; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 409AB;
9:45-11:15am

Chair: *Mustafa Yunus Eryaman, Canakkale Onsekiz Mart University*

Participants: *Marit Honerød Hoveid, Norwegian University of Science and Technology; Stefanie Y. Chye, Singapore University of Social Sciences; Yuto Kitamura, University of Tokyo - Hongo; Tracy X. P. Zou, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Alberto Ramirez Martinell, Universidad Veracruzana, Mexico; Miriam Fábila Alves, Associação Nacional de Pesquisa e Pós-Graduação em Educação (ANPED); Tony Hall, University of Galway; Natasha Ziebell, University of Melbourne; Motlalepule Ruth Mampane, University of Pretoria*

Division Sessions

92.016. Celebrating 15 years of Herstories: (Re)membering Black Women's Leadership Then and Now. Division A - Administration; Symposium
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Santa Barbara C; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Breaking Through the Concrete Ceiling: Black Women in Academic Leadership at Elite Research Universities. *Wanda J. Blanchett, Rutgers University*

Leading from the Shield: The Legacy of Black Women's Leadership and Sorority Life. *Janeula M. Burt, Bowie State University; Dr Erinn Fears Floyd, Equity and Excellence in Education, LLC and Texas State University*

A Praise song for Herstories: Reflecting on the Lessons of Black Women's Leadership in Urgent Times. *Durell M. Callier, University of Delaware; Dominique C. Hill, Colgate University*

From Hidden Treasure to Superwoman: Leveraging M.A.P.S. to Navigate the Trajectory and Sustainability of Black Women in Public K-12 Educational Leadership. *LeTrecia M. Gloster, School District of the City of York*

Black Women's Activism and Leadership as the Blueprint for Visioning Black Girl Futures. *Courtney Mauldin-Jones, Syracuse University*

Resilient Herstories: Leading from the Periphery with Purpose, Power, and Possibility. *Patrice A. McClellan, The Ronald Group*

Chair: *Dominique C. Hill, Colgate University*

Discussant: *Judy A. Alston, Miami University (OH)*

92.017. Diverse Voices in Educational Leadership. Division A - Administration; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Level 2, Mt. Washington; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

When the Game is Unsafe and Biased: School Leaders Experiences with Race and High School Athletics. *George Theoharis, Syracuse University; Christine Elaine Ashby,*

Syracuse University; Sean Drake, Syracuse University; Lauren Ashby, Syracuse University; ParKer Bryant, Syracuse University

Stakeholder Perceptions of Four-Day School Weeks: Leadership and Policy Implications in K-12 Education. *Kathryn Washington, Lamar University; Janice L. Taylor, Lamar University; Frances Martinez-Perez, Lamar University*

Comparing Teacher and Principal Perceptions of Support in Rural Schools. *Henry Tran, University of South Carolina; David Osworth, University of North Carolina - Greensboro; Valerie Yelverton, University of South Carolina; Suzy Hardie, University of South Carolina*

The Eye of the Beholder: Principal-Teacher Perceptual (In)Congruence in Transformational Leadership and Teacher Satisfaction. *Soobin Choi, The Education University of Hong Kong*

Principals' Zhongyong Thinking And Teachers' Career Adaptability: A Moderated Serial Mediation Model. *Yufeng Zhang, Beijing Normal University; Min Qi, Beijing Normal University*

Chair: *Kimberly Jamison, University of North Carolina - Wilmington*

Discussant: *Priya Goel, California State University - Dominguez Hills*

92.018. Exceptional Leadership: Administrative Considerations for Special Education and Student Success. Division A - Administration; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Los Feliz; 9:45-11:15am
Participants:

Organizing for Inclusion: Do Fast-Growth Districts' Systematic Approaches Facilitate or Constrain Principals' Efforts? *Barbara L. Pazez, University of North Texas; Pinyi Wang, University of Florida; April Miles, Texas State University*

Redefining Principal Preparation: Centering Emotional Labor, Special Education, and Communication for Inclusive Leadership. *Catherine E. Olver, Gonzaga University*
Special Education Administrators' Problem-Solving and their Institutional and Organizational Responses to the COVID-19 Crisis. *Corrine Aramburo, University of New Mexico*

Striving for Graduation for All: High School Administrator Decision Making on Credit Recovery. *Samantha L. Viano, George Mason University; Hector Moya, George Mason University; Vivian Conner, George Mason University; Elissa Robinson, George Mason University*

Transforming Systems for Inclusion: Advancing Reform for Students with Disabilities. *Aashna Khurana, Boston College*
Discussant: *Joan Schumann, International MTSS Association*

92.019. Re/Visioning Leadership for Critical and Transformative Changes in Schools. Division A - Administration; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, La Brea; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- Transformational Leadership, Principal Self-Efficacy, and Organizational Learning: Rethinking Humility and Overconfidence in School Leadership. *Sedat Gümüş, The Education University of Hong Kong; Jiafang Lu, The Education University of Hong Kong; Koksai Banoglu, The Education University of Hong Kong; Allan David Walker, The Education University of Hong Kong*
- Expanding a Multidimensional View of Equity: Reimagining Futures for Principal Decisions and Practice around Student Identity. *Jasper Lucas, University of California - San Diego; Joni Kolman, California State University - San Marcos*
- Justice in the Balance: How School Leaders Navigate Discipline Decisions. *Jeff Walls, University of Iowa; Akenten Dwamena, University of Iowa; Sharon D. Kruse, Washington State University - Vancouver*
- Mediating and Navigating Complex Changes and Influences: Successful Principal Leadership in the United States. *Rose M. Yilmaki, Northern Arizona University; Betty M. Merchant, University of Texas - San Antonio; Lauri Johnson, Boston College; Jingping Sun, University of Alabama*
- Chair: *Xiu Cravens, Vanderbilt University*
Discussant: *Marcia Theresa Caton, Molloy University*

92.020. Designing Engaging Learning Environments: Insights from AI, VR, and Games. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, San Gabriel B; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- Are All Engagement Types Related to Successful Learning in Game-based Learning Environments? *Maral Karimi, University of Central Florida; Megan Wiedbusch, University of Central Florida; Natalie Blaize, University of Central Florida; James C. Lester, North Carolina State University; Roger Azevedo, University of Central Florida*
- Can AI Instructional Agents Better Foster Student Engagement? A Multimodal Neurophysiological Comparison with Human Teachers. *Xiaobo Liu, Tsinghua University; Zhanxin Hao, Tsinghua University; Jifan Yu, Tsinghua University; Fei Qin, Tsinghua University; Zhiyuan Liu, Tsinghua University; Yu Zhang, Tsinghua University*
- Multidimensional Modeling of Multimodal Learner Engagement and Emotion during Game-Based Learning. *Megan Wiedbusch, University of Central Florida; Matthew Moreno, University of Central Florida; Cameron Marano, University of Central Florida; Milouni Patel, University of Central Florida; James C. Lester, North Carolina State University; Roger Azevedo, University of Central Florida*
- One Log, Two Stories: How Learning Order Shapes the Interpretation of VR Log Events. *Taehyun Kim, Utah State University; Zifeng Liu, University of Florida; Wanli Xing, University of Florida; Tonmoy Roy, Utah State University*
- Promoting University Students' Creativity and

Entrepreneurship: An AI-Powered Scenario-based Design Thinking Approach. *Chenguang Du, The Education Uni; Shen Qiao, The Education University of Hong Kong*

Chair: *Chaewon Kim, Florida State University*

92.021. Emotions and Emotion Regulation in Mathematics: New Insights Into Antecedents And Outcomes. Division C - Learning and Instruction Cosponsored with SIG-Motivation in Education; Symposium
Westin Bonaventure, Level 3, Avalon; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- Happiness/Joy Mediates The Effect of Story Problem Difficulty on Arithmetic Strategy Sophistication in Kindergarten. *Traci Shizu Kutaka, University of Virginia; Pavel Chernyavskiy, University of Virginia; Julia Pfeiffer, University of Virginia*
- Emotion Regulation During Complex Mathematics Problem Solving: Testing the ERAS Model with Elementary Students. *Krista R. Muis, McGill University; Kelsey M. Losenno, McGill University*
- Running Away From Math? Analyzing STEM Choice for the Study Program. *Maristella Lunardon, University of Tuebingen; Christina Artemenko, University of Tübingen; Serena Rossi, Loughborough University; Hans-Christoph Nürk, University of Tübingen; Krzysztof Cipora, Loughborough University*
- Dynamic Self-Concept and Emotional Responses: Insights from a Situated Laboratory Study in Mathematics. *Franziska Eckerskorn, Ludwig-Maximilians-University Munich; Anne C. Frenzel, University of Munich; Jonathan Fries, University of Vienna; Miriam Wünsch, University of Munich; Sara Laybourn, Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität München; Christoph Niepel, University of Luxembourg; Thomas Goetz, University of Vienna*
- How Growth Mindsets Shape Emotional Support, Math Anxiety, and Achievement in Low-Achieving Students. *Katharina Asbury, Leibniz Institute for Science and Mathematics Education; Ricarda Steinmayr, Technische Universität Dortmund; Lisa Charlotte Benckwitz, Leibniz Institute for Science and Mathematics Education; Bastian Carstensen, Leibniz Institute for Science and Mathematics Education*
- Chairs: *Katharina Asbury, Leibniz Institute for Science and Mathematics Education; Franziska Eckerskorn, Ludwig-Maximilians-University Munich*
Discussant: *Reinhard Pekrun, University of Essex*

92.022. Heterogeneity in Multilingual Children: Language Skills and Experiences, Home Literacy Environment, and Learning Contexts. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Symposium
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, San Gabriel A; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Profiles of Language and Reading Experiences of Spanish-

English Emergent Bilinguals in Dual Language Immersion Programs. *Becky H. Huang, The Ohio State University; Ye Shen, Johns Hopkins University*

Literacy Instructional Time and Content Coverage: Variation by Multilingual Learner Composition in Elementary Classrooms. *Jackie E. Relyea, North Carolina State University; Michael J. Kieffer, New York University*

Student Profiles of Foundational Literacy Skill Abilities in English and Spanish. *Carlin Conner, University of Virginia; Sarah Wellberg, University of Virginia; Veronica Mellado De La Cruz, University of Virginia; Emily J. Solari, University of Virginia; James Soland, University of Virginia; Marcela Courtade Carlock, University of Virginia*

Bilingual Home Literacy Profiles and their Associations with Language and Literacy Skills. *Marc Goodrich, Texas A&M University; Jiali Wang, University of California - Irvine; Rhea Pai, Texas A&M University; Lisa Fitton, Florida State University*

Chair: *Ye Shen, Johns Hopkins University*

Discussant: *Patrick Proctor, Boston College*

92.023. The new, the familiar, and the unfamiliar: Expanding your research outlets. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Symposium
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Beaudry B; 9:45-11:15am

Chairs: *Dionne Cross Francis, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Alison C. Koenka, University of Oklahoma*

Participants: *Marcus Johnson, University of Arkansas at Little Rock; Daniel Dinsmore, University of North Florida; Sharon L. Nichols, University of Texas - San Antonio; Jason C. Chow, Vanderbilt University; Stephanie Anne Shelton, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*

92.024. Innovation in Cross-National Critical Thinking Assessment: AI Integration, and Innovations in Performance-Based Measurement. Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Symposium
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 7th Floor, Hollywood Ballroom I; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Using Multivariate G-Theory to Examine Rater and Source Effects in Cross-Country Critical Thinking Performance Assessment. *Roza Nalbandyan, Stanford University; Richard J. Shavelson, Stanford University*

Measurement of Critical Thinking: The quality of LLM-based essay coding of Performance Assessment Tasks. *Kai S. Cortina, University of Michigan; Jackson Schwartz, University of Michigan; Blake Ebricht-Jones, Washington University in St. Louis*

How Critically Do Students Engage with AI? *Natalia Ronderos, University of Zurich; Doreen Flick-Holtsch, University of Zurich; Julian Patricio Mariño von Hildebrand, Universidad de los Andes; Maren Oepke,*

University of Zurich

University Students' Source Evaluation and Argumentation: Comparing Performance and Processes through Essays and Think-Alouds. *Katharina Depré, Johannes Gutenberg University of Mainz; Olga Zlatkin Troitschanskaia, Johannes Gutenberg University of Mainz; Dominik Braunheim, Johannes Gutenberg University of Mainz; Thiemo Hagen, Johannes Gutenberg University of Mainz; Richard J. Shavelson, Stanford University*

Chair: *James W. Pellegrino, University of Illinois at Chicago*

Discussant: *Patricia A. Alexander, University of Maryland*

92.025. Visual Thinking Strategies: An Expansive Method for Qualitative Inquiry. Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Symposium
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Hancock Park West; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Images of Hope. *Marva Cappello, San Diego State University*
Critically Analyzing Dominant Images of Teaching. *Kris Bell, Claremont Graduate University*

Transborder Pedagogy: Preparing Critically Conscious Border Educators through Visual Thinking and Translanguaging at the Imperial Valley Borderlands. *Vannessa Falcón Orta, San Diego State University*

Looking Together: Visual Thinking Strategies as Black Feminist Praxis in Youth Participatory Research. *Autumn A. Griffin, University of North Carolina - Charlotte*
Voices on the Inside. *Reka C. Barton, University of Maryland VTS and the Black Girl Gaze. Darielle Blevins, Arizona State University*

Chair: *Reka C. Barton, University of Maryland*

Discussant: *Marva Cappello, San Diego State University*

92.026. Learning Environments and Academic Growth in Diverse Contexts. Division E - Counseling and Human Development; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304A; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Cultivating Holistic Growth: Investigating Social-Emotional Competencies and STEM Identity in Rural Chinese Fifth Graders. *Leyao Xing, University of California - Davis; Weicong Lyu, University of Macau; Jiarun Lai, University of Columbia; Yaqi Wang, Yuzhang Normal University; Ying Xu, Harvard University*

Home and School Factors Associated with Math Trajectories Before and After COVID-19 in Ghana. *Clara-Christina Gerstner, University of Alabama; Noelle Suntheimer, University of Pennsylvania; Emily M. Weiss, Fordham University; Richard Appiah, Harvard University; Elisabetta Aurino, University of Barcelona; Sharon Wolf, University of Pennsylvania*

The Collective Effects of Daily Social Support on Adolescent

School Engagement: A Dynamic SEM Approach. *Suyoung Kim, University of Chicago; Jiwon Kim, Northwestern University*

The Role of Parental Math Skills and Affect on Children's Numeracy and Spatial Math Skills. *Jazelle Pilato, University of Pittsburgh; Nandini Rastogi, University of Pittsburgh; Joei Angelina Camarote, University of Pittsburgh; Nathaniel Philip Pettit, University of Pittsburgh; Elizabeth Votruba-Drzal, University of Pittsburgh; Melissa Libertus, University of Pittsburgh; Heather J. Bachman, University of Pittsburgh*
Chair: *Miguel Angel Garcia-Bocanegra, Northwestern University*

92.027. Bloodlines on the Leaves: Afrofuturist Storyworlding at the Edge of the End of the World. Division G - Social Context of Education; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 303A;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Afrofuturistic Noir. *Kenjus T. Watson, American University*
Place and Time in Black Studies. *Nina Monet Reynoso, University of Colorado - Colorado Springs*
Critical Fabulation within and Against the Archive. *Mary Senyonga, Sacramento State University*

Chair: *Daniel Gilbert Solorzano, University of California - Los Angeles*

Discussant: *Daniel Gilbert Solorzano, University of California - Los Angeles*

92.028. Language Across Borders: Multilingual Realities and Linguistic Justice in Global Classrooms. Division G - Social Context of Education; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 306B;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

"I Feel Our Situation is Completely Different!" Persisting Monolingual Ideologies Among International School Egyptian Teachers. *Alia Shalaby, Pennsylvania State University*

Language in Reading Research: The Case of a Middle-Tier English-Medium Private School in Pakistan. *Saulat Pervez, International Institute of Islamic Thought*

Pláticas as Pedagogy: Fostering Linguistic Consciousness Among Latinx Youth. *Elisa Marisol Serrano, University of Texas - San Antonio*

Chair: *Elisa Marisol Serrano, University of Texas - San Antonio*
Discussant: *Noor Ali, Northeastern University*

92.029. Unapologetically Centering Youth in Theory, Practice, and Praxis. Division G - Social Context of Education; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 301B;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Performativity in the Lifeworld: How Youth Assert Their

Identity in the Shadow of Legislative Erasure. *Benjamin Lebovitz, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Beyond Fidelity: Enacting YPAR through a Decolonial Feminist Praxis. *Rosalinda Godinez, Cleveland State University; Taylor Zepp, Cleveland Metro Schools*

Who Benefits from Bullying Prevention? How Policy Shapes the Stratification of Youth Conflict. *Sarah Miller, Boston University*

"It's Different Here": Racial Climate and Belonging Across School and Community Contexts for Immigrant-Origin Youth. *Sophia Rodriguez, New York University; Melissa Ortiz, New York University*

We Deserve It: Informing Literacy Instruction through Black Youths' Educational Beliefs. *Glenda Chisholm, Georgia State University*

Chair: *Barbara Thelamour, Swarthmore College*

Discussant: *Karena Alane Escalante, The Education Trust*

92.030. "Asian and Latinx Anti-Blackness in Schools and Communities: Complicity and Resistance" Book Discussion Symposium 2. Division G - Social Context of Education; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 303B;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Unforgetting Anti-Blackness: Latinx Pedagogy and Strategies for Inclusive Classrooms. *Myrlene Jean-Venant, Bridgewater State University*

Anti-Blackness in Latinx communities in a (mainly) U.S. Context. *Melina Melgoza, Harvard Graduate School of Education; Manuel Gochez, LAUSD*

A "Racial Identity Shaped by Loss and Feeling Lost": AfroLatine Student Experiences Navigating Identity Binarization. *Natalie King-Shaw, Harvard Medical School; Sam King-Shaw, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Melanie Sonsteng-Person, Salem State University; Dominique Mikell Montgomery, University of Nevada - Reno; Alexia Oduro, University of Southern California; Tiffany Hogan, MGH Institute of Health Professions*

The Terrible Sticky Truths of Aligning with Whiteness: A Story of Anti-Blackness and Self-Erasure. *Cristina C. Santamaria Graff, Indiana University - Indianapolis; Mercedes Adell Cannon, Indiana University - Indianapolis*

Relearning Positionality Through Teaching Anti-Blackness: A Critical Autoethnography from a Middle Eastern Educator. *Haniyeh Kheirkhah, Pennsylvania State University*

Chair: *Brittany A. Aronson, Pennsylvania State University*

Discussant: *Hannah R. Stohry, Bridgewater State University*

92.031. Advancing Educational Research for All with Large-Scale School Assessment Data: Insights from Innovative Approaches. Division H - Research, Evaluation and Assessment in Schools; Symposium
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Boyle

Heights; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Identifying Navigation Behavioral Patterns with Time Warped Longest Common Subsequence on Process Data. *Qiwei He, Georgetown University; Binhui Chen, Georgetown University*

Preliminary Development of a Mathematics Engagement Composite Using NAEP Process Data of Eighth-Grade Students. *Antranik T Kirakosian, Washington State University*

Response Time-Informed Multiple Imputation: Comparing IRT-, MICE-, and Autoencoder-Based Approaches for Planned Missing Data. *Surina He, University of Alberta; Peter van Rijn; Usama S. Ali, Educational Testing Service*

Toward Human-Centered Explainable AI Applications for Generating Feedback for Classroom Teachers from Large-Scale Assessments. *Hongwen Guo, Educational Testing Service; Matthew S. Johnson, Educational Testing Service; Luis Enrique Saldivia, ETS; Michelle Worthington, ETS; Jeremy Lee, ETS; Kadriye Ercikan, Educational Testing Service*

Comparative Analysis on Item Difficulty Predictions Between National and International Assessment Programs. *Mubarak O. Mojinyinola, University of Iowa; Olasunkanmi James Kehinde, Norfolk State University; Judy H. Tang, Westat*

Chair: *Judy H. Tang, Westat*

Discussant: *Shenghai Dai, Washington State University*

92.032. Centering Equity and Belonging: Transforming Outcomes Across Higher Education.

Division J - Postsecondary Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum H; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

STEM Journeys: A Cross-Case Analysis of STEM Scholarship Student Experiences Across Three Regional Higher Education Contexts. *Maria L. Espino, University of California - Los Angeles; Elizabeth Meza, University of Washington - Seattle; Debra D. Bragg, Bragg & Associates, Inc; Will Tyson, University of South Florida*

Rethinking Faculty Roles in Student Success: Examining Graduation Outcomes at Minority-Serving Institutions. *Yuriko Sato, University of Wisconsin-Madison*

Beyond the Mission: Institutional Strain and the Human Cost of Student Support at HBCUs. *Jorge Burmicky, Howard University; Arsene Frederic, Howard University; Darieon Laurell McFadden, Howard University; Erinn Carter, Howard University; Kathleen M. Rzucidlo, Howard University; Tatianna Dupierier, Howard University*

Data-Informed and Equity-Driven Approaches to Institutional Transformation: Exploring Uses of Racial Climate Assessments. *Sylvia Hurtado, University of California - Los Angeles; Gabriel Gutierrez Aragon, University of California - Los Angeles; David Ulises Vargas Ezquivel, University of*

California - Los Angeles; Marcelo Alonso Almora Rios, University of California - Los Angeles; Amanda Carrasco, University of California - Los Angeles; Denise Ortiz, University of California - Los Angeles

Chair: *Stephanie Luna-Lopez, University of California - Davis*

92.033. Corequisite Mathematics Reform in Practice: Faculty Roles, Curricular Change, and Student Experience

Across States. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Symposium

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum I; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Instructor Buy-In and Instructional Practice in Corequisite Mathematics Reform: Evidence from a Mixed-Methods Study of Virginia Community College System. *Daman Chhikara, University of California - Irvine; Zachary Beamer, Virginia Community College System; Mina Sajjadi, University of Delaware; Laura M. Desimone, University of Delaware; Di Xu, University of California - Irvine*

How AB 705 Reshaped College-Level Placement, Completion, and Academic Progression in California. *Loris Fagioli, Irvine Valley College; XunFei Li, University of California - Irvine; Di Xu, University of California - Irvine; Yumeng Zhang, University of California - Irvine*

Resistance or Reception: Understanding the Patterns of Corequisite Implementation Across the Nevada System of Higher Education. *Stefani Relles, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Ariana Lucia Garcia, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Federick Ngo, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*

Student Perspectives on Corequisite Reform: Student Experiences with Instructional Practice and Institutional Change at CUNY. *Andrea Lopez Salazar, Teachers College, Columbia University; Selena Cho, Community College Research Center; Julia Raufman, Teachers College, Columbia University; Elizabeth Kopko, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Chair: *Di Xu, University of California - Irvine*

Discussants: *Federick Ngo, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Lauren Schudde, University of Texas at Austin; Lindsay Daugherty, RAND Corporation*

92.034. Equity and persistence among students of color.

Division J - Postsecondary Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum G; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Beyond the Ban: Contextualizing the Erasure of Black Student Voices in the Discourse on "Race-Neutral" Policies in Higher Education. *Mya Haynes, USC; Desiree O'Neal, University of Southern California*

Transfer Student Experiences by Race, First-Generation Status, and Family Income. *Jeongsan Hwang, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Karla Velasco, University of Illinois*

at Urbana-Champaign; Yasamin Khoshpour, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Gianina R Baker, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Lorenzo D. Baber, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign

Activism is “Acknowledging Oppression and Caring to Create Change”: An Educational Case-Study Exploring Graduate Student Critical Consciousness. *Stephanie Cuellar, Texas Christian University; Pablo Montes, Texas Christian University*

Examining the Racialized Experiences of Black Women in Peer Interactions in Active Learning Science Classrooms. *Hannah Nichols, University of Georgia; Talia Swanson, University of Georgia; Renette Tchockski, University of Georgia; Jordan Roberts, University of Georgia; Matthew Turnipseed, University of Georgia; Dona Raju, University of Georgia; Valencia Kelly, University of Georgia; Chase Anderson, University of Georgia; Tatiane Russo-Tait, University of Georgia*

Discussant: *Paris D. Wicker, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

92.035. The Grad School Escape Room: Decoding Doctoral Survival. Division J - Postsecondary Education;

Demonstration/Performance

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum F; 9:45-11:15am

Participant:

The Grad School Escape Room: Decoding Doctoral Survival. *Gaurav Harshe, University of South Carolina; Janay Georgetta Crosland, North Carolina State University; Sarah A. Hale, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

Chair: *Sarah A. Hale, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

Participants: *Gaurav Harshe, University of South Carolina; Janay Georgetta Crosland, North Carolina State University; Sarah A. Hale, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

92.036. Amplifying HBCU Educator Impact: From Research to Practice in Teacher Diversity and Equity. Division K -

Teaching and Teacher Education; Symposium

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 9; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Let's Get to Work: Helping Parents and Community Members Advocate for Black Teachers. *Meredith Anderson, United Negro College Fund; Ashlyn Thomas, UNCF*

Exploring how four HBCU Teacher Education programs fortify the Black Teacher Pipeline. *Keeley Copridge, Frederick D. Patterson Research Institute*

Funding and Amplifying HBCU-Trained Educators in K–12 Classrooms. *Tito Soto-Carrion, DonorsChoose*

Chair: *Laura McGowan-Robinson, Diversity in Leadership Institute*

Discussant: *Laura McGowan-Robinson, Diversity in Leadership Institute*

92.037. Crossing Borders: Immigrant, Migrant, and

Transnational Teacher Identities. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 7; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Gendered Meanings of Teaching and Professional Commitment among Turkish Muslim Migrant Women Teachers. *Esra Bozkurt, University of California - Santa Cruz*

Choosing Korean, Reclaiming Chicano Spanish: A Critical Linguistic Autoethnography of Discursive Language Ideologies and Multilingual Identity Construction. *Kevin Perez, New York University*

Migrant Teachers of Color in U.S. Schools: A Review of Literature. *Seungwoo Hwang, Michigan State University*

Tapping Into Our Transnational and Translingual Assets: A Collaborative Autoethnography of Asian International Teaching Assistants. *Yangyang Zhu, Purdue University; Woongsik Choi, Illinois State University; Tirtha Karki, Purdue University*

Chair: *Esra Bozkurt, University of California - Santa Cruz*

Discussant: *Neisha Terry Young, Stony Brook University - SUNY*

92.038. Exploring Teacher's Perceptions & Experiences With the Adoption of AI in Education. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 8; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Enhancing AI teaching competency in vocational education through an AI-TPACK-based professional development approach. *Wenxin Guo, Tsinghua University; Qi Wu, Syracuse University*

Imagining Possibilities of an Artificial Intelligence Instructional Coach: Qualitative Evidence from District and Schools. *Yuxi Wen, Michigan State University; Ao Qu, Massachusetts Institute of Technology; Jiayi Zhang, National University of Singapore; Alok Prakash, Massachusetts Institute of Technology; Andrés Salazar-Gomez, Massachusetts Institute of Technology; Paul Liang, Massachusetts Institute of Technology; Jinhua Zhao, Massachusetts Institute of Technology*

Rural-Urban Teachers' Differences in Perceptions and Usage of Applying Generative AI in Teaching Practices. *Shuo Feng, Shanghai Jiao Tong University; Xin Gao, Shanghai Jiao Tong University; Mingjie Li, Shibe District Education Research and Development Center, Qingdao; Qiyu Zhang, Shandong Normal University; Siqi Shen, Vanderbilt University; Yangcun Feng, Tongji University; Shuai Wang, Shanghai Jiao Tong University*

Chair: *Qiuying Wang, Oklahoma State University*

Discussant: *Vivek Sabanwar, Texas A&M University*

92.039. From Dashboards to Dialogues: Reimagining Teacher

Preparation through AI, Media Literacy, and Transnational Partnerships. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 1;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Comparing Teacher and LLM Feedback as Dialogic Practice. *Lena Phalen, Stanford University; Mei Tan, Stanford University; Christopher Mah, Stanford University; Dora Demszky, Stanford University*
Cultivating Courage, Creativity, and Critical Thinking: Professional Development in Media Literacy to Address Violent Extremism. *Renee Hobbs, University of Rhode Island; JOHN Palella, Brown University; Kent Lenci, Middle Ground School Solutions*
Learning Analytics Dashboards for Adaptive Teaching: What Teachers Need to See. *jingyi Qiao, University of Twente; Mohammadreza Farrokhnia, University of Twente; Tessa Eysink, University of Twente*
Mentoring EFL Pre-Service Teachers in AI-Assisted Practicum: Benefits and Challenges. *Mega Wulandari, The Ohio State University*
Reimagining Teacher Learning: A Transnational CoP-RPP Model for Intercultural Pedagogy in Virtual Space. *Soyoung Han, Cyber Hankuk University of Foreign Studies; Yun-chen Yen, Pennsylvania State University; Seongryeong Yu, Old Dominion University*

Chair: *Katrina Arndt, St. John Fisher College*

Discussant: *Zhaochen Gu, University of Illinois at Chicago*

92.040. Sankofa: Reflecting on What We Have (un)Learned in Teaching and Teacher Education. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 6;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Sankofa: A Current VP's Reflection on What We Have (un)Learned in Teaching and Teacher Education. *Kimberly A. White-Smith, University of San Diego*
Sankofa: A Former VP's Reflection on What We Have (un)Learned in Teaching and Teacher Education (2013). *A. Lin Goodwin, Boston College*
Sankofa: A Former VP's Reflection on What We Have (un)Learned in Teaching and Teacher Education (2010). *Etta R. Hollins, University of Missouri - Kansas City*
Sankofa: A Former VP's Reflection on What We Have (un)Learned in Teaching and Teacher Education (2004). *Christine E. Sleeter, California State University - Monterey Bay*

Chairs: *Nicol R. Howard, Chapman University; Erica D. McCray, University of Florida*

Discussants: *Erica D. McCray, University of Florida; Nicol R. Howard, Chapman University*

92.041. A Critical Examination of School Board Governance Models: Imagining a Better Future. Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 10;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

How Should School Boards Govern?: Visions from Three Board Governance Models. *Sarah Diem, University of Missouri; Erica O. Turner, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Christina Bustos, Arizona State University*
“Qui bono?”: The Impacts of Lone Star Governance on Districts and School Boards. *Rachel Sue White, University of Texas at Austin; Christina Bustos, Arizona State University; Lolita A. Tabron, University of Denver*
Student Outcomes Focused Governance in Seattle: Gaps in Student Outcome Data and Troubling Narratives in Practice. *Carrie Sampson, Arizona State University; Ronnie Angel Chavez, Arizona State University; Audrey Amrein-Beardsley, Arizona State University; Margarita Pivovarova, Arizona State University; Grace Louise Beall, Arizona State University*
Validating a Survey Instrument to Assess School Board Members' Perceptions of Texas's Lone Star Governance (LSG) Model. *Brandon J. Yuhas, Arizona State University; Audrey Amrein-Beardsley, Arizona State University; Margarita Pivovarova, Arizona State University; Grace Louise Beall, Arizona State University*
Technocratic or Democratic? How Data Cultures Shape Success, Decision-Making, and Accountability in School Board Governance. *Lolita A. Tabron, University of Denver; John Matthew Fredericks, Arizona State University; Ashley Yung Batchelor, Arizona State University*

Chair: *Rachel Sue White, University of Texas at Austin*

Discussant: *Richard Blissett, University of Maryland - Baltimore County*

92.042. At The Intersection of Schools, Housing Policy, Neighborhood Change, and Social Capital. Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 2;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Fragmented Systems, Disconnected Schools: Student Homelessness in a County Governance Landscape. *Earl J. Edwards, Boston College*
Gentrification and School Diversity: Reconstituting Segregation in the Era of “Choice”. *Elizabeth I. Rivera, Montclair State University*
Implementation Network Mapping: Examining Equity and Voice in Detroit's Choice Neighborhood Initiative. *Tara Blagg, University of Southern California; Megan Connors, University of Michigan; Daniel Espinoza, University of Southern California; Kara S. Finnigan, University of Michigan; Huriya Jabbar, University of Southern*

California; DeMarcus A Jenkins, University of Pennsylvania; Sarah Winchell Lenhoff, Wayne State University

Social Capital in the Shadow of Redevelopment: Navigating Education in Changing Neighborhoods. Sarah Winchell Lenhoff, Wayne State University; Huriya Jabbar, University of Southern California; Margaret Dawson-Amoah, University of Southern California; Ayana Cheyenne Colvin, University of Pennsylvania; Angelica Ramirez, Wayne State University; DeMarcus A Jenkins, University of Pennsylvania; Kara S. Finnigan, University of Michigan

Where Housing Meets Education: The Role of Integrated Support in Advancing Educational Equity for Black Families. Ayana Cheyenne Colvin, University of Pennsylvania; DeMarcus A Jenkins, University of Pennsylvania; Samantha Bello, University of Pennsylvania

Chair: Cassandra Rubinstein, North Carolina State University
Discussant: Kendall Dwayne Deas, University of South Carolina

SIG Sessions

92.043. Translanguaging as Embodied Language Policy in Critical Inquiries about Linguistic Justice Across Generations and Contexts. SIG-Bilingual Education

Research; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 306A;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Children as Language Policymakers through their Translanguaging Practices in a Dual Language School. Daniel Garzon, California State University - Los Angeles
High School Newcomer Youth as Language Policymakers: Translanguaging in a Multilingual Student Advisory Council. Adria Padilla-Chavez, University of Colorado - Boulder; Laura Meinzen, University of Colorado - Boulder; Deborah K. Palmer, University of Colorado - Boulder; Michelle Renée Valladares, University of Colorado - Boulder

Translanguaging with Heritage Zapotec Speakers in a Community-Based Language Revitalization Study Abroad. Laura Meinzen, University of Colorado - Boulder; Raichle Farrelly, University of Colorado - Boulder; Ambrocio Gutiérrez Lorenzo, University of Colorado - Boulder

Teacher Inquiry: Educators Path to Policymaking and Advocacy for Bilingual Learners. Teresa Bruno Warkentin, University of Colorado - Boulder; Deborah K. Palmer, University of Colorado - Boulder

Translanguaging as a Tool for Liberatory Organizing. Jenna Cushing-Leubner, University of Wisconsin - Whitewater; Natalia Benjamin, Rochester Public Schools

Chairs: Daniel Garzon, California State University - Los Angeles;
Laura Meinzen, University of Colorado - Boulder
Discussant: Jonathan Rosa, Stanford University

92.044. Practicing Restorative Justice: Preparing Aspiring Educators to Transform Schools Using Anti-Racist Strategies. SIG-Critical Educators for Social Justice;

Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304C;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Practicing Restorative Justice as an Anti-Racist Educator. Erika Strauss Chavarria, Columbia Community Care

Fostering Healthy Racial Identity in the Early Years: Making Black Lives Matter in ECEC. Denisha Jones, *Defending the Early Years*

Community-Based Instruction as a Pathway to Belonging, Voice, and Citizenship for Students with IDD. Winter Marshall-Allen, *The Homer Organization for More Equitable Relations*

Anti-Racism for White Educators - Disrupting White Supremacy in Ourselves and our Systems. Terry Jess, *Juanita High School*

Chair: Erika Strauss Chavarria, Columbia Community Care

Discussant: David O. Stovall, University of Illinois at Chicago

92.045. Black Women's Brunch. SIG-Critical Examination of

Race, Ethnicity, Class and Gender in Education; Reception
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 502A;
9:45-11:15am

Chair: Jemimah L Young, Texas A&M University

92.046. Aliveness, Abolition, and Affirmation: Actualizing Audre Lorde's Commitment to a "Livable Future" in Early Education. SIG-Critical Perspectives on Early

Childhood Education; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 309;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Expecting Encounters: Incorporating Black Aliveness into Early Childhood Research. Candice Love, University of Maryland

Beyond Agents of Carcerality: Portraits of Black Male Teachers Enacting Prison Abolition Literacies. Nathaniel Bryan, University of Texas at Austin

Centering Children of Incarcerated Caregivers: A Critical Content Analysis of Children's Emotions in Picture Books. Emma Williams, Santa Clara University; Brita A. Bookser, Santa Clara University

Teaching to Eradicate Carceral-Educational Entanglements: Introducing Dispositions of Womanist Anti-Carceral Praxis in Early Childhood Education. Brita A. Bookser, Santa Clara University

Chair: Brita A. Bookser, Santa Clara University

Discussant: Rachel McMillian, Indiana University - Indianapolis

92.047. Untold Lessons from History: Teacher Interviews and Archival Records from the Perry and Abecedarian Projects. SIG-Early Education and Child Development;

Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Plaza I;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- A Deeper Dive into Perry Preschool: The Influence of Teacher's Home-based Visits in Children's Learning. *Tomoko Wakabayashi, Oakland University; Jill Claxton, HighScope Educational Research Foundation*
- Rediscovering Perry Preschool through Archival Classroom Records and Teacher Interviews. *Sylvi Kuperman, University of Chicago; Tomoko Wakabayashi, Oakland University*
- A Mixed-Methods View of the Carolina Abecedarian Project: Applying Educators' Voices to Explaining Adult Outcomes. *Kylie L. Garber, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Sylvi Kuperman, University of Chicago*

Chair: *Sylvi Kuperman, University of Chicago*

Discussants: *Alison Baulos, University of Chicago; Louise Derman-Sparks, Pacific Oaks College*

92.048. Dreamweaving Our Radical Elsewhere: Black and Indigenous Women in Educational Leadership on Healing and Purpose. SIG-Educational Change;

Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum J;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- Kinship and Coalition: Black and Indigenous Women's Leadership in Education for Critical Hope and Healing. *Whitneé L. Garrett-Walker, University of San Francisco; Jasmine Pham, University of Toronto - OISE; Nia Spooner, University of Toronto*
- The Politics of Refusing to Die - A Reflective Narrative Inquiry About Black and Indigenous Survival Despite Continued Neo-Colonial Violence In the Academy. *Ciann L. Wilson, Wilfrid Laurier University*
- Creating New Intellectual Traditions Through Indigenous and Black Educational Collaborations. *Megan Scribe, Toronto Metropolitan University*
- Working from the community within the community: A personal Black and Indigenous Feminist perspective on building an educational grassroots project. *Kayla Webber, University of Toronto*

Chair: *Vidya Shah, OISE/University of Toronto*

Discussant: *Vidya Shah, OISE/University of Toronto*

92.049. Rethinking Learner Engagement in the Age of Intelligent Systems. SIG-Instructional Technology; Paper Session

Westin Bonaventure, Level 2, Echo Park; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- The Ephemeral Power of Analytics: Tracing Multi-Dimensional

Engagement in Social Annotation Over Time. *Yeonji Jung, Texas A&M University; Sophia Soomin Lee, University of Florida; Alyssa Wise, Vanderbilt University*

"Are you studying?": Investigating college students' self-regulated learning process across scheduled study events with mobile nudges. *Zilu Jiang, Johns Hopkins University; Meng-Ting Lo, National Yang Ming Chiao Tung University; Jingwen He, University of North Texas; Zilong Pan, Lehigh University; Kui Xie, University of Missouri*

Emotional Incongruency in Pedagogical Agents: The Superior Impact of Positive Tone Over Positive Visuals. *Shufan Yu, The Hong Kong Polytechnic University; Qingtang Liu, Central China Normal University; Ruiqiu Ye, Central China Normal University; Suxiao Xu, University of Hong Kong; Ping Li, The Hong Kong Polytechnic University*

Exploring Learner Autonomy Through Chatbot Mode Selection: Interaction Patterns and Learning Outcomes in an Online Course. *Songhee Han, Florida State University*

How Mentors Shape Preservice Teachers' Interest in Computational Thinking: The Influence of Mentor Orientations. *Yuanhua Wang, West Virginia University; Ugur Kale, Indiana University; Melissa Beth Sherfinski, West Virginia University*

Chair: *Susie Gronseth, University of Houston*

92.050. Language Brokering in Diverse Contexts: Implications for Schools. SIG-Language and Social Processes;

Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304B;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- Language Brokering at the Doctor During COVID-19: An Asian American College Student's Autoethnography. *Gloria Choi*
- The Relationship Between Language Brokering and Citizenship Becoming: Implications for K-12 Education. *Lisa M. Dorner, University of Missouri; Sujin Kim, George Mason University*
- From Family Helper to Business Facilitator: Reconceptualizing Child Language Brokering Through Communication Accommodation Theory. *Krissia Martinez, University of Texas at Austin*
- Co-Constructing Narratives of Language Brokering and Learning through Digital Discourse. *Flora Zempleni, University of California - Los Angeles*
- Leveraging Language Brokering: A Researcher-Teacher Partnership for Designing Language Brokering-Based Classroom Learning. *Jackson Gzehoviak, University of California - Los Angeles; Sarah Perez, University of California - Los Angeles*

Chair: *Lisa M. Dorner, University of Missouri*

Discussant: *Marjorie E. Faulstich Orellana, University of California - Los Angeles*

92.051. Advances in Learning Environments Research. SIG-Learning Environments; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Georgia I;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- Exploring Student Agency Across Multiple Perspectives.
Margaret Vaughn, Washington State University
- How University Innovation Climate Shapes Graduate Research Behavior: Chain Mediation via Creative Self-Efficacy and Achievement Motivation. *Xiaolan Mo, East China Normal University*
- Hybrid Learning and Recognition: A Case Study on Workplace Learning in Vocational Education. *Michael Smits, Curio; Tom Adams, KWIC*
- More Than Meets the Eye: Pluri-perspective Dialogues and 'Seeing' in Museum Spaces. *Agni Stylianou-Georgiou, University of Nicosia*
- STEM teacher education: Integrating Indigenous knowledges and place-based pedagogical environments. *Kevin O'Connor, Mount Royal University*

Chair: *Christopher S. Long, University of North Texas*

92.052. Critical Race Perspectives in Education. SIG-Multicultural/Multiethnic Education: Theory, Research and Practice; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Georgia II;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- Exploring Publications about Anti-racism in Academic Journals During a Time of Poly Crisis. *Estella Chizhik, California State University - Long Beach; Tamika Lovelace, San Diego State University; Alexander W. Chizhik, San Diego State University*
- Challenging Raciolinguistic Ideologies: Asian-American Students' Stories of Resistance and Resilience. *Chaehyun Lee, Southeastern Oklahoma State University*
- Erasing the Margins: Kurdish Scholars' Voices on the Erosion of Academic Freedom in Turkey. *Clarisse Halpern, Florida Gulf Coast University; Hasan Aydin, Florida Gulf Coast University*

Chair: *Martha Rosas, Lehman College - CUNY*

Discussant: *Tu Dang, University of Georgia*

92.053. Freire's Radical Utopia: Denouncing the Historical Moment and Announcing Solidarity and Activism in Academia. SIG-Paulo Freire; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Los Cerritos; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- Recognizing Rohr's Wisdom Pattern through a Freirean Lens in Negotiating the Zeitgeist of our Times. *James D. Kirylo, University of South Carolina; Darrell Boyd, Eastern University*
- Critical pedagogy from Indigenous philosophical notions on the

hatred of equality. *Raul Olmo Fregoso Bailón, University of Nevada - Reno*

Freirean Praxis and Feminist Intersectionality: A Dialogue for Transformative Democracy. *Sheila L. Macrine, University of Massachusetts - Dartmouth*

Beyond-Humans Reinventions of Criticality and Freirean Ecopedagogy: Posthumanist Disruptions of the Anthropocene and Wicked Problems. *Greg William Misiaszek, Tohoku University*

De-"Banking" Citizen Research in a Postdigital Era: Postdigital Citizen Research as Critical Pedagogy. *Sara E. Tolbert, Monash University; Petar Jandric, Polytechnic of Zagreb; Michael Jopling, University of Brighton; Sarah Hayes, Bath Spa University*

Chair: *Inny Accioly, Universidade Federal Fluminense*

92.054. Learning to Fight, Fighting to Learn: Secondary Student Actors Reclaiming Mathematics Through Histories of Resistance. SIG-Research in Mathematics Education; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum A; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- Exploring Quantification for Advocacy: Student Perspectives on Public Policy in a Summer Mathematical Modeling Seminar. *Nathan Alexander, Howard University*
- Math as Resistance: Students' Epistemic Authority and Engagement in a Critical Mathematics Classroom. *Patricia Buenrostro, University of Illinois at Chicago*
- Intellectual Safety in Mathematics: Secondary Student Perspectives from an Anti-Racist Summer Institute. *Jennifer Aracely Rodriguez, University of Michigan Ann Arbor; Jennifer Randall, University of Michigan*
- Reimagining Mathematics through the Voices of Queer High School Students. *Weverton Ataide Pinheiro, Texas Tech University*

Chair: *Charles Mack Phillips, University of Michigan*

Discussant: *Kari Kokka, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*

92.055. Personal / Emotional Relevance in Student Science Learning. SIG-Science Teaching and Learning; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, San Fernando; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- "Because if we wouldn't imagine, we'll all be extinct": Communities and Contestations in Imaginative Placemaking. *Hannah H. Ziegler, Vanderbilt University; Heidi Carlone, Vanderbilt University; Lauren Connelly, Vanderbilt University*
- Emotions for Social Change: Fostering Critical Emotional Awareness During Climate Learning. *Imogen Herrick, University of Kansas; Michael A. Lawson, Kansas State University*

(Counter)Mapping in Science Education: Bridging Physical and Cultural Geographies Through Youth Ethnography. *Victoria Henry, Teachers College, Columbia University; Colby Tofel-Grehl, Teachers College, Columbia University; Tyler Hansen, Washington State University; Melissa Mendenhall, Utah Valley University; Candace Penrod, Columbia University*

Exploring Identity Dynamics in Socioscientific Issues-Based Science Education in Chinese Secondary Schools. *Tiantian Wang, King's College London*

Middle School Student Perspectives on Science Identity During a Storyline Unit that Integrated Critical Consciousness. *Sarah E. Fogelman, Boston College; Maria A. Moreno Vera, Boston College; Ji Sun Ham, Taunton Public Schools; Katherine L. McNeill, Boston College*

Chair: *Alicia Cotabish, University of Central Arkansas*

92.056. Rooted in History, Emboldening the Future: Scoping the SEL Implementation Literature and Enacting Statewide Change. SIG-Social and Emotional Learning; Symposium
Westin Bonaventure, Level 3, Santa Monica B; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

A Scoping Review of SEL Implementation Literature to Identify Conditions For Systemic SEL Implementation. *Valerie Shapiro, University of California - Berkeley; Tiffany M. Jones, Colorado State University; Addison Duane, Sacramento State University; Kamryn Morris, University of Washington; Ashley Metzger, University of California - Berkeley*

Approaches to Equity in Systemic SEL Implementation Research: A Scoping Review of the Literature. *Valerie Shapiro, University of California - Berkeley; Tiffany M. Jones, Colorado State University; Addison Duane, Sacramento State University; Kamryn Morris, University of Washington; Ashley Metzger, University of California - Berkeley*

Educational Leader Reports of Change in SEL Implementation Conditions Statewide over One Year of CalHOPE. *Ashley Metzger, University of California - Berkeley; Justin D. Caouette, University of Washington; Patrick Robinson-Link, University of California - Berkeley; Jax Braun, University of Washington; CalHOPE Research Committee, University of California - Berkeley; Valerie Shapiro, University of California - Berkeley*

Chair: *Mai Xi Lee, Sacramento County Office of Education*

Discussant: *Todd Herrenkohl, University of Michigan*

92.057. Emotion, Justice, and Curriculum. SIG-Social Studies Research; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Plaza II; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

A Critical Discourse Analysis of Emotions and Affect in U.S. History Curriculum Frameworks. *Brittany Jones, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

Learning, Healing, and Belonging Together: Co-Constructing Third Space with Asian American and Migrant Youth through Youth Participatory Action Research. *Yeji Kim, University of Missouri*

Unforgetting histories to teach for climate justice and sustainability. *Anne Marie Kavanagh, Dublin City University; Caitriona Ni Cassaithe, Dublin City University*
“When I Became a Black Woman:” Ethnopoetry and Curricular Unforgetting for Social Studies Education. *Danielle Charlemagne, University of Georgia*

Chair: *Anna Yonas, University of Kansas*

Discussant: *Christopher C. Martell, University of Massachusetts - Boston*

92.058. Beyond Traditional SEM: Model Fit, Heterogeneity, and New Paradigms. SIG-Structural Equation Modeling and Multilevel Modeling Methods; Paper Session
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Echo Park; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Factored Structural Equation Modeling in Blimp. *Craig K. Enders, University of California - Los Angeles*

Fit Index Criteria for Multisample SEM with Ordinal Data. *Suat Babayigit, University of Miami; Stephen A. Sivo, University of Central Florida*

Nonnormality and a Small Latent Class in Growth Mixture Modeling. *Emma Elisa Evudóttir, University of South Florida - Tampa; Eunsook Kim, University of South Florida; Courtney Howard-Kirby, University of South Florida; Xilong Jing, University of South Florida; Xin Tong, University of Virginia; Yan Wang, University of Massachusetts Lowell; David Goretzko, Utrecht University*

Segmented Change in Latent Variables: A Second-Order Structured Latent Curve Model for Time-Structured Count Data. *Jeff Harring, University of Maryland; Marian Strazzeri, US Food and Drug Administration; Nan Bernstein Ratner, University of Maryland*

The Impact of Replacing First-Order Latent Factors with Composite Scores on Model Fit and Structural Estimates in SEM. *Chunhua Cao, University of Alabama; Justice Dadzie, University of Alabama; Theode Niyirinda, University of Alabama*

Chairs: *Eunsook Kim, University of South Florida; Emma Elisa Evudóttir, University of South Florida - Tampa*

92.059. Critical and Equity-Focused Perspectives on AI in Education. SIG-Technology as an Agent of Change in Teaching and Learning; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum B; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Equity and AI in the K-12 Curriculum: How Preservice Teachers Develop Critical Understandings. *Lauren Weisberg, University of Texas - Arlington; Christine Wusylko, Kennesaw State University; Kara M. Dawson, University of Florida*

Critical AI in Education Pathways: Towards a Human Centered AI for Teacher Educators. *Evrin Baran, Iowa State University; Melis Dilek, Iowa State University; Melika Ziba, Iowa State University*

Toward Equitable and Socially Just Artificial Intelligence in Education: A Scoping Review and Bibliometric Analysis. *Yao Fu, University of Wisconsin - Whitewater; Zhenjie Weng, Duke Kunshan University; Jiayi Wang, University of Wisconsin-Stevens Point*

Chair: *Lauren Weisberg, University of Texas - Arlington*
Discussant: *Natalie B. Milman, The George Washington University*

Division and SIG Roundtables

92.060. AERA Roundtable Session Sunday 9:45 am;
Roundtable Session

92.060-1. Building from our Histories and Transforming Future Methodologies and Pedagogies in EdD programs (Table 1). Division A - Administration; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Co-Constructed Knowledge and Collective Care: The Promise of Communities of Practice in EdD Programs. *Amaarah N. DeCuir, American University; Pete Locher, American University; Ambereen Khan-Baker, National Education Association; Rachel Cason, American University*

A Kitchen Table Talk: Reimagining the Process of Doctoring Ourselves. *Elizabeth Holliday Morgan, Morgan State University; LaToya Jackson, Sierra College; Sheeva Sabati, California State University - Sacramento; Rachel Stewart, Los Rios Community College; Vajra M. Watson, University of Redlands; Ximena Ospina, California State University*

Radical Imagination in Action: Black Feminist Pedagogy, Podcasting, and Humanizing Leadership in an EdD Program. *Monique Lane, Saint Mary's College of California; Scott Drain, De La Salle High School; Kenneth Farr, Salesian College Preparatory; Candace Jones, Saint Mary's College of California; Omar Sanchez, Saint Mary's College of California; Lakshmi Warriar, Saint Mary's College of California*

Chairs: *Elizabeth Montaño, University of California - Davis; Rosaisela Rodriguez, University of California - Davis*

Discussant: *Jill Alexa Perry, Carnegie Project on the Education Doctorate*

92.060-2. Developing Reflective Leadership Practices: Mentoring, Feedback, and Well-Being (Table 2). Division A - Administration; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Developing Leadership Through Inquiry and Reflection: Lessons from a University-District Preparation Partnership. *Shanna Dawn Anderson, Montclair State University; Donna Volpe, Ramsey Board of Education; Rachel Garver, Montclair State University*

From Praise to Procedures: Topic Modeling the Content and Context of Principal Feedback. *Zixi Chen, NYU Shanghai; Jihyun Kim, Sungshin Women's University; Xintong Li, University of Missouri*

Mindful Leadership: Exploring the Role of Mindfulness in Cultivating Adaptive and Resilient School Leaders. *Gerald Maraia, Brooklyn College - CUNY; Pedro J. De La Cruz Albizu, Brooklyn College - CUNY*

Reimagining Early Childhood Educator Leadership: Disrupting Hierarchies in Ontario's Full-Day Kindergarten. *Samia Javed, University of Western Ontario*

92.060-3. Curriculum, Identity, and Resistance: Navigating Gender in Archives and Classrooms (Table 3). Division B - Curriculum Studies; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Teacher Decision-Making: Understanding Gender Identity Content (GIC). *Greg Knotts, California State University - Northridge*

The Mythology of Manhood: Curriculum, Truth, Subjectivity, and Reparation. *James P. Burns, University of New Mexico*
"The Oppressed Never Revere Their Oppressors": Womanist Diasporic Pedagogy in the Archives of Claudia Jones. *Cortnie Belser, CUNY Graduate Center*

Chair: *Sherry L. Deckman, CUNY, Lehman College and Graduate Center*

92.060-4. Towards an Anti-racist Pedagogy (Table 4). Division B - Curriculum Studies; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Not More Reform, We Need an Epistemic Revolution: Theorizing Epistemic Oppression in U.S. Mathematics Education. *Kiruba Murugaiah, Boston College*

Book talk: Racism in the Enacted Curriculum: Agentic Ideas and the Spaces Between. *Alexander B. Pratt, University of Memphis*

Curriculum as Spatial: Rethinking Educational Policy through Black Geographic Thought. *Gabrielle M. Warren, University of Toronto - OISE*

92.060-5. Revolutionary transformation of the decolonial curriculum to come (Table 5). Division B - Curriculum Studies; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- Joy as (R)evolutionary Praxis: Centering Young Women of Color in Curriculum Transformation. *Chinyere Ngozi Harris, Teachers College, Columbia University*
- Reimagining Higher Education: Transformation through Culturally Responsive Curriculum. *LeeAnne McNulty, Allan Hancock College; Rick Rantz, Allan Hancock College*
- The Fight for Poly Perspectivity: A Call for Multicultural Curriculum Legislation. *Fabiola Quinones, Teachers College, Columbia University*
- Transforming Conditions of Lovelessness: A Critical Inquiry into Radical forms of Love in Education. *Celine Vallejo Norman, The University of Texas at Austin*
- Critically Dreaming Curriculum Otherwise: Collective Storytelling through Justice-Oriented Pedagogies. *Dianne T. Wellington, SUNY - College at Cortland; Alycia M. Elfreich, Montana State University*

Chair: *Celine Vallejo Norman, The University of Texas at Austin*

92.060-6. The Challenges and Possibilities of Teacher Leadership: International Perspectives (Table 6). SIG-Leadership for School Improvement; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- Conceptualizing Teacher Leadership: Issues and Evidence. *David M. Gurr, University of Melbourne*
- The Case of the United States: The Need for Critical Teacher Leaders. *Jill Bradley-Levine, Ball State University; Gilbert C. Park, Ball State University*
- The Case of Singapore: Shaping the Future of Teacher Leadership. *Salleh Hairon, National Institute of Education, Nanyang Technological University*
- The Case of China: Promoting Teacher Leadership through Professional Learning Communities. *Qi Xiu, South China Normal University; Kailun Zhou, South China Normal University*
- The Case of Australia: Team Enactment of Teacher Leadership in Whole School Improvement. *Dorothy Andrews, University of Southern Queensland; Joan Margaret Conway, University of Southern Queensland*

Chair: *Peter Wiens, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*

92.060-7. Race, Identity And Temporality In Decolonial Education (Table 7). SIG-Decolonial, Postcolonial, and Anti-Colonial Studies in Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- Lever, Wedge, Screw: Simple Machines of Decolonization, a Homegrown Framework. *Linda Orie, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Aydin Bal, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Dian Mawene, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Morgan Mayer-Jochimsen, University of Wisconsin - Madison*
- A Time for Justice: Restorative Justice, Temporality, and Hospitality. *Daniel Thalkar, University of San Diego*
- 'The World We Should Be Working Towards': Radical Imagination, Identity, and Decoloniality in Undocumented Organizing. *Alejandra Pérez, University of Washington*
- From Model Minority to MAGA: Indian American Republicanism and the Politics of Racial Identity. *Madhavi Tandon, University of Colorado - Denver*

Chair: *Yaa Dankwa, The Ohio State University*

92.060-8. Black Christian Identity and Praxis: Past and Present (Table 8). SIG-Religion and Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- Holy Words, Hidden Histories: Black Religious Publishing and the Pedagogy of Liberation. *Patricia Haggler, York College, City University of New York*
- More Than Belief: A FaithCrit Exploration of Black Christian Scholar Identity. *Erica T. Campbell, Miami University (OH); Philip Michael Thomas, Miami University (OH); LaKisha Zyyon, Miami University (OH)*
- Centering Faith at the Margins: A FaithCrit Analysis of Black Women Multicultural Center Administrators. *Erica T. Campbell, Miami University (OH); Philip Michael Thomas, Miami University (OH)*

Chair: *Katherine M. Ward, Michigan State University*

92.060-9. Educator Workforce and Practice and AANHPI Communities (Table 9). SIG-Asian Americans and Pacific Islanders in Education and Research; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- Asian American Native Hawaiian Pacific Islander (AANHPI) K-12 Educators: A Systematic Review of Their Experiences. *Lillie Ko-Wong, University of California - San Diego; Willa Mei Kurland, UCLA; Kourtney Kawano, University of California - Berkeley*
- Culturally Responsive Practices Among Chinese Male Childcare Professionals in the United States. *Qiong Wu, California State University - Los Angeles; Davyn Jones, Cornell University; Su-Jeong Wee, California State University - Los Angeles; Wook Yang, California State University Los Angeles; Yafen Lo, California State University - Los Angeles*

From Pattern to Pedagogy: Integrating Traditional Chinese Design into Anti-Racist Computer Science Education. *Xinyue Zhou, Michigan State University; Michael L. Lachney, Michigan State University*

Chair: *Yih-Jium Shen, The University of Texas Rio Grande Valley*

92.061. AERA Roundtable Session Sunday 9:45 am - Gold 1;
Roundtable Session

92.061-1. Community College Transfer (Table 1). Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Where Agentic and Aspirational Momentum Grows and Slows in Community College Transfer. *Nicole B. Contreras-Garcia, Florida Atlantic University*

When Neutrality Masks Power: Transfer Rates as Traces of Hegemonic Whiteness in Los Angeles Community Colleges. *German C. Jimenez, University of San Diego*

Pathways and Place: Examining the Geography of Opportunity in Transfer Choice Sets. *Carmen Serrata, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Catherine Hartman, North Carolina State University; Joanna D. Sanchez, Excelencia in Education; Cathy Howell, University of North Carolina - Charlotte*

92.061-2. Addressing Campus Climate and Representation Issues in Higher Education (Table 2). Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Bull-Headed Administration: Chief Academic Officers' Perceptions of Presidential Bullies and Campus Climate. *Leah P. Hollis, Pennsylvania State University; Gala Sofia Campos Oaxaca, Pennsylvania State University*

Experiences of Six Indigenous Women Scholars in British Columbia: An Anishinaabe Case Study on the Impacts of Institutional Culture and Workload on Wellness. *Ursula Katic-Filis, University of Calgary*

Latinx Staff and Faculty Labor and Impact at California and Colorado Hispanic-Serving Institutions. *Yazmin Alexandra Perez, Claremont Graduate University; Elizabeth Lopez, Claremont Graduate University*

We Will Not Be Quiet: Exposing White Allyship, Erasure, and Black Women's Institutional Trauma. *Ayana T. Hardaway, Stanford University; Patrice Renee, Thomas Jefferson University; Brittany N. Glover, San Diego State University; Janelle L. West, Rutgers University*

Women's Representation in Higher Education Leadership: A Mixed-method Analysis of Enablers and Barriers. *Özlem Baykan, Middle East Technical University; Merve Zayim-Kurtay, Middle East Technical University*

Chair: *Jawaria Ashraf, Temple University*

92.061-3. Beyond the College Walls: Instustry Collaborations Research Productivity and Internationalization in Higher Education (Table 3). Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Global alignment, local challenges: Reimagining research capacity in Azerbaijani higher education. *Leyla Jabbarzade, University of Sheffield*

What Affects the Quality of Industrial Partners' Relationship with Universities in Implementing Teaching-focused University-industry Collaboration. *Tengteng Zhuang, Beijing Normal University*

92.061-4. From Deficits to Assets: Designing Inclusive and Collaborative Educational Practices (Table 4). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Collaborating Across Classrooms: Empowering Writers and Future Teachers through Digital Biographies for Women's History Month. *Jessica Tobin Nagle, Saint Joseph's University*

Deleting deficits and building bridges: Using community-based pedagogy with *cariño* to build positive epistemologies. *Pedro A. Berlanga, University of Texas at Austin; Cinthia S. Salinas, University of Texas at Austin; Robert L Sobel, The University of Texas at Austin; Perri Sweed, University of Texas at Austin*

Disparities in Math Teachers' Collective Responsibility and English Learner Outcomes: A National Longitudinal Study. *Guillermo Lopez, Claremont Graduate University*

Reimagining Assessment in PBL: Welcoming Dandelions and Designing Culturally Sustaining Protocols for CLD Learners. *Emma H. Cho, University of Washington*

Chair: *Jessica Tobin Nagle, Saint Joseph's University*

92.061-5. Curriculum as a Site of Struggle, Collaboration, and Transformation (Table 5). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Reimagining Science Teaching: Promoting teacher agency through a research-practice partnership for Bee Hunting convergent research. *Isabel Delgado, University of Puerto Rico - Río Piedras; Sara Ocasio, University of Puerto Rico - Río Piedras; Joseph Carroll, University of Puerto Rico - Río Piedras; Jose Soto, University of Puerto Rico - Río Piedras; Ariana Rodriguez, University of Puerto Rico - Río Piedras;*

Lizbeth Alvarado, University of Puerto Rico - Río Piedras; Jose Agosto, University of Puerto Rico - Río Piedras; Martin Geria, University of Puerto Rico - Río Piedras

Teacher Leadership in World Languages—To What End? Perspectives of U.S. Teacher Educators. *William Davis, University of Oklahoma; Brianna Janssen Sánchez, University of Kentucky*

Wading through Confusion, Trusting through Uncertainty: Igniting teacher power through collaborative curriculum building. *Hilary Naa-Afi Tackie, SUNY - College at New Paltz*

Beyond Compliance: Teachers' Lived Experiences and the Making of Ethnic-Racial Identity Projects in K-12 Education. *Julia Callegari, Northwestern University*

Chair: *Sabrina Leigh Caldwell, University of South Alabama*

92.061-6. Examining Positioning and Identity: Making Meaningful Change from the Margins (Table 6). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Critical Reflexivity and Asian American Teachers: Navigating Identity and Critical Consciousness in AAPI Curriculum. *Minkyung Choi, Montclair State University; Sharon Lai-LaGrotteria, Montclair State University*

Towards Understanding Muslim Teachers' Professional Identity: Survey and Scale Development. *Nushrat Hoque, Florida International University; Manar Hussein, Montclair State University; Maheen Ahmad, Montclair State University; Mayida Zaal, Montclair State University; Amir Billups; Chedia Ayari, Montclair State University; Nagla Bedir, Perth Amboy Public Schools*

Positioning a Volunteer Chinese Teacher in an American Heritage School: A Narrative Inquiry Approach. *Ying Hu, Capital Normal University; Qianqian Ma, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

Chair: *Rupam Saran, Medgar Evers College - CUNY*

Discussant: *Rupam Saran, Medgar Evers College - CUNY*

92.061-7. Affective Climates in Teaching: Optimism, Discipline, and Retention (Table 7). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Education in the Post-Truth Era: Southeast Nigeria's Conflict Between Ideological Indoctrination and Critical Thinking. *Christopher Obiyo, Patrise Inc.*

Latent Profile Analysis of Teacher Academic Optimism: Patterns and Variation by Educational Track and Experience. *Ruud Lelieur, University of Antwerp; Bea Mertens, Antwerp University*

Supporting and Retaining Teachers in the Profession: K-means

Clustering Analysis of Teacher Profile Survey Data. *Ha Eun Kim, University of California - Los Angeles (Center for the Transformation of Schools); Erika Yagi, University of California - Los Angeles; Stanley L. Johnson, University of California - Los Angeles*

Why Excellent Teachers Take Root in the Rural Area: From the Perspective of Emotional Geographies Theory. *Wanpeng Lei, Central China Normal University; Zihan Wang, The Chinese University of Hong Kong*

Why Was She Being Punished? *Danqin Chen, East China Normal University*

Chair: *Christopher Obiyo, Patrise Inc.*

92.061-8. Beyond Access: How Policy, Data, and Tools Shape Students' Educational Opportunities (Table 8). Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Roundtable Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

The Role of Shadow Education in an Independent Elementary School: Perspectives from Key Stakeholders. *Nicole Alexandra Del Oso, Florida International University; Jacqueline Lynch, Florida International University*

Beyond Access: English Learner Students' Enrollment in and Completion of Advanced High School Coursework. *Nami Shin, University of Kansas; Karen D. Thompson, Oregon State University; Ilana M. Umansky, University of Oregon; Janette Dalila Avelar, University of Oregon*

Framing Reform & Discourse: An NLP and Organizational Analysis of STEM Education Logics and Reformers' Positionality. *Jose Roman Aguilar, University of California - Berkeley*

Multiple Definitions, One Pathway? How CTE Coursetaking Criteria Shape Concentrator Classification and Student Outcomes. *Jennifer A. Freeman, Texas Tech University; Jacob Kirksey, Texas Tech University; Angela Crevar, Mercer University; Braden Reed, Texas Tech University*

The Effects of An Automatic Notification Tool to Increase Participation in Advanced High School Courses. *Megan Austin, American Institutes for Research; Michael Kruse, American Institutes for Research; Matthew J. Farmer, American Institutes for Research; Preeya Pandya Mbekeani, American Institutes for Research; Sara Mitrano, American Institutes for Research*

Chair: *Amanda Slaten Frasier, East Tennessee State University*

92.061-9. Revisiting the Record: Policy Historiographies and the Making of Educational Futures (Table 9). Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Roundtable Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Policy Evolution and Educational Equity for English Language Learners: A Case Study from Florida Schools. *Naila Peken,*

University of South Florida

Shaping Türkiye's Educational Research: Bridging Historical Depth with Future-Focused Methodologies. *Kamil Arif Kirkic, Istanbul Sabahattin Zaim Universitesi*

The Future of Equity, Diversity, and Inclusion (EDI) in Education: Keep, Reform, or Dismantle? *Ardavan Eizadirad, Wilfrid Laurier University*

92.062. AERA Roundtable Session Sunday 9:45 am - Gold 2;
Roundtable Session

92.062-1. Disparities and Differences: Examining Charter Schools Outcomes (Table 1). Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Variation in English Learner Achievement Across Charter and Traditional Public Schools. *Hana Kang, University of Colorado - Colorado Springs; Dick M. Carpenter, University of Colorado - Colorado Springs*

Continuing the Great Debate: Illuminating Discipline Disparities in Texas Charter and Traditional Public Schools. *Nikita Azinnia McCree, University of Missouri; Katherine A. Graves, Utah State University; Ambra Green, University of Texas - Arlington; Kelvin Tosin Afolabi, University of Texas at Arlington*

For-Profit vs. Nonprofit Charter School Performance: A Comparison of Student Achievement Across CMO and EMO Charter Schools in Arizona. *Adel Arghand, University of Utah*

“And so, we sit amongst the survivors”: Centering Black and Latino/a/x families' narratives of race, place, and choice in suburban New Jersey. *Olga Correa, Grinnell College*

Chair: *Eupha Jeanne Daramola, University of California - Irvine*

92.062-2. Contested Opportunities: Power, Place, and Educational Justice (Table 2). Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Disrupting Histories of Displacement: Whiteness as Property and the Battle for Educational Resources Amid Redevelopment. *Erika L. Davis, University of Michigan*

How the Middle to High School Transition Can Shape Dual Enrollment Opportunities. *Eric Loken, University of Connecticut; Julia Oas, University of Connecticut; Alexandra J. Lamb, University of Connecticut; Olcay Yavuz, Southern Connecticut State University; Morgaen L. Donaldson, University of Connecticut*

“I Am Because We Are”: An Ubuntu Perspective on Teacher Motivation in Ghana's Low-Fee Private Schools. *David Kyei-Nuamah, East China Normal University; Xingyuan*

Gao, East China Normal University

Opportunity Hoarding Across Context: Contribution to Theory and Practice. *Idit Fast, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev; Yariv Feniger, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev; Shira Klimor Maman, Bar Ilan University*

"That's When It Hit Me": Origin Stories of Building Transformative Solidarity in Educational Organizing. *Michiko Hikida, The Ohio State University; Laura A Taylor, Rhodes College; Kushya Sugarman, Mount Holyoke College; Melissa Schieble, Hunter College - CUNY; Amy Vetter, University of North Carolina - Greensboro; Kristen L. Hodnett, Hunter College - CUNY; Athriyana Pattiwael, The Ohio State University*

Chair: *Anna Louise Baird, California State University - Dominguez Hills*

Discussant: *Tanishia Lavette Williams, Brandeis University*

92.062-3. Envisioning Arts Curriculum Futures (Table 3). SIG-Arts and Learning; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

“Bringing out Hidden Qualities”: Teachers' Descriptions of Emergent Student Leadership within Brilliant Storytellers Program. *Lisa DaVia Rubenstein, Ball State University; Kathrin Maki, University of Florida; Sasha Hatfield, University of Florida; Lisa M. Ridgley Smith, University of San Diego; Alisa Scherbakova, University of Georgia; Theadora Vlaamster, Ball State University*

Restorying as a Tool to Reimagining Theatre Design Curriculum for Transformative Futures. *Joselyn F Ludtke, Rockford Public Schools; Joshua Rashon Streeter, University of Texas at Austin*

Feminista Art Epistemology: An Anzaldúa and Duchamp Convergence for Transformative Visual Knowledge Production. *Nora E. Rodriguez, University of Texas - San Antonio*

University-High School Partnership: An Evaluation Study. *Robert D. Hannafin, Fairfield University; Lori Jones, Fairfield University; Katie Lang, Fairfield University*

Reimagining Civics Through the Arts: Place, Pedagogy, and Participatory Curriculum Design. *Minki Jeon, Florida State University*

Chair: *Azmi Azam, University of Arizona*

92.062-4. Civic Education and Literacy (Table 4). SIG-

Democratic Citizenship in Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Increasing Literacy through Civic Education. *Diana Owen, Georgetown University*

Unlocking Civic Potential: ICCS-Based Mixed-Methods Insights from Socioeconomically High-Need Schools in

Germany. *Rukiye Ates, University Duisburg - Essen; Nina Charlotte Johanna Welsandt, University of Duisburg-Essen*
Writing Democracy Anew: LGBTQ+ Youth Letters as Acts of Civic Imagination. *Avner Rogel; Avner Rogel, Teachers College, Columbia University; Oren Pizmony-Levy, Teachers College, Columbia University*

92.062-5. Experiential Education and Community

Engagement: Scholarship and Practice SIG Roundtable 3 (Table 5). SIG-Experiential Education and Community Engagement: Scholarship and Practice; Roundtable Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Engaged Learning and Student Preparedness for Post-Graduate Plans and Experiences. *Eilene A. Edejer, Loyola University Chicago; Mia Jasmine Martinez, Loyola University Chicago; Leah Marie Pope, Loyola University Chicago*

Enhancing Experiential Learning through IT Partner Collaborations for Student Equity and Career Readiness. *Vanessa Hammler Kenon, University of Texas - San Antonio; Peppy Garner, University of Texas - San Antonio; Cristian Aldrete, The University of Texas San Antonio*

From Campus to Classroom: Teacher Candidates Bringing Community-Based Learning Theory to Life. *Christian Winterbottom, University of North Florida; Caran Mullins, Duval County Public Schools*

Data Art in Place: Youth-Designed Community Inquiry as a Model for Community-Engaged Learning. *Chulin Chen, University of Tennessee; Amy Maples, University of Tennessee; Lynn L. Hodge, University of Tennessee*

Chair: *Theresa Dawson, Pepperdine University*

Discussant: *Elizabeth Dunens, University of Minnesota - Rochester*

92.062-6. Of Care and Resistance: Teachers' Voices in Complex Times (Table 6).

SIG-Lives of Teachers; Roundtable Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Carrying the weight alone: First-year teachers, support gaps, and the burden of self-care. *Allison Hitchens, University of South Florida - Tampa*

Centering Teacher Sensemaking: An Approach to Designing Social Justice Curricular Adaptations. *Kierstin M. Giunco, University of Cincinnati; Michelle Nguyen Kwok, Texas A&M University*

Out of Bounds: Secondary Teachers' Use of Labor Boundaries as a Strategic Form of Resistance. *Shanea Neal, Southern Methodist University; Janel Anderson, Gonzaga University; Jeff Walls, University of Iowa*

Where is the Love?: A Systematic Review of Love among Black Teachers. *Zariah Nicole, Johns Hopkins University*

92.062-7. Advancing Equitable Pedagogies Through Cross-Curricular and Cross-Context Partnerships (Table 7).

SIG-School-University Partnership Research; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

From Fragility to Sustainability: Advancing Educational Equity through a School-University Partnership in Jordan. *Susan L. Ogletree, Georgia State University; James Badger, University of North Georgia; Juman Al Bukhari, University of North Georgia; Subhi Jamal Almuqraa, Georgia State University*

Partnerships and Progress: Summer Learning Partnerships for Equitable Literacy Development. *Earlisha Jenkins Whitfield, University of Central Florida; Taiel Lucile, University of Central Florida*

Teacher Teaming as Job-Embedded Professional Development: Results of a Fidelity of Implementation Study. *Injila Rasul, University of Massachusetts - Amherst; Rebecca H. Woodland, University of Massachusetts - Amherst*

The Ethnic Studies-Heritage Spanish Project: Partnering to Explore Crosscurricular Possibilities in Politicized Times. *Eduardo Rafael Munoz-Munoz, San José State University; Margaret Peterson, Stanford University; Amado M. Padilla, Stanford University; Vicky C. Xiong-Lor, California State University - Fresno*

Future for "Grow Your Own" Teachers Programs: Learning and Listening to Youth Voices. *Shereen Aly Mohamed Sayed, University of Georgia; Morgan Faison, University of Georgia; Matthew Nyaaba, University of Georgia; Brandi N. Hinnant-Crawford, Clemson University*

Discussant: *Lina Safa, Pepperdine University*

92.062-8. Exploring Inclusive Teaching Practices through Self-Study (Table 8).

SIG-Self-Study of Teacher Education Practices; Roundtable Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Best Practice as Barrier Rather than Bridge: Navigating Tensions Within Myself and With My Students. *Kristina J. Doubet, James Madison University*

Rooted in Reflection: Reimagining SEL in Early Childhood Education. *Allison Jane Barness, University of Northern Iowa; Brandy A. Smith, Wartburg College; Allison Pattee, University of Northern Iowa*

The implications for self and students through exploring inclusive practices in teacher preparation. *Leigh A. Kurz, Susquehanna University; Valerie A. Allison, Susquehanna University*

Toward Foundations 3.0: Conducting A DisCrit Audit of Our Introductory Education Course. *Rob Martinelle, Boston*

University; Brigid Rowlings, Boston University
Chair: Rob Martinelle, Boston University

92.062-9. Culturally Responsive Approaches to Equity in STEM+CS (Table 9). Division C - Learning and Instruction; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Making Mr. Evil French Cheetoh: In-school Makerspace Symbiotic Learning and Play of two Intersectionally-marginalized Girls. *J.C. Leapman, University of California - Davis; Lee Michael Martin, University of California - Davis; Kurt Winsler, University of California - Davis*

Culturally Responsive-Sustaining Education in Computer Science: Linking Teachers' Practice to Student Outcomes. *Xia Li, Research Alliance for New York City Schools; Cheri Fancsali, Research Alliance for New York City Schools; Kathryn Hill, Research Alliance for New York City Schools; Alexandra Adair, The College Board*

Effects of Motivational Climate on Motivational Beliefs in Computer Science: A Longitudinal Analysis. *Zeynep Ambarkutuk, Virginia Tech; Brett D. Jones, Virginia Tech*

Growth Mindset Beliefs During Engineering Internships: An Empirical Study of Undergraduate Women Students. *Jing (Crystal) Zhang, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Emma M. Mercier, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

From Overwhelmed to Empowered: How Professional Development in Culturally Relevant Computer Science Lifts Up Public School Teachers. *Daniel L. Hoffman, University of Hawai'i at Manoa; Seungoh Paek, University of Hawai'i at Manoa; Peter Leong, University of Hawai'i at Manoa; Rochelle Pi'ilani Kaaloo, University of Hawai'i at Manoa*

Chair: Cecilia D Craig, Independent Researcher

92.063. AERA Roundtable Session Sunday 9:45 am - Gold 3; Roundtable Session

92.063-1. Allocating and Sustaining Resources for School Improvement (Table 1). SIG-Fiscal Issues, Policy and Education Finance; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Allocating Resources for School Improvement: A Multiple - Case Study. *Carlas L. McCauley, Howard University*

Enhancing Financial Literacy Among School Principals. *Alejandra Garibay, Galt Unified School District; Anyisia P. Mayer, California State University, Stanislaus*

Fiscal Cliff or Soft Landing? Exploring District Responses to Expiring COVID-19 Relief Funds. *Bryan Beverly, Michigan State University; Tyler Thur, Michigan State University; Jacqueline Gardner, Michigan State University; Abigail*

Bies, Michigan State University

How Are Federal Resources Determined to Support School Improvement Strategy? Understanding SEA's Funding Allocation Processes. *Carlas L. McCauley, Howard University*

Chair: Jie Lin, Shanghai Jiao Tong University

92.063-2. Reimagining School Improvement: Research, Policy, and Practice in a Changing Educational Landscape (Table 2). SIG-School Effectiveness and School Improvement; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Generative Artificial Intelligence and the Future of Educational Administration, Organization, and Leadership: A Systematic Review. *Jianmin Li, Beijing Normal University; Yuting Wang, Beijing Normal University; Mingyu Ma*

Teacher Agency in Collaborative Practices: An International Scoping Review. *Papa Kobina Enyimah Moses, Brigham Young University; Bryant Jensen, Brigham Young University*

From Data to Action: Predicting School Accountability Outcomes to Guide Targeted Interventions. *Jose Garza, Region 1 Educational Service Center; Jeffery Chernosky, Texas A&M University - Kingsville; Kelly S. Hall, Texas A&M University - Kingsville; Robert Ayala, Texas A&M University - Kingsville; Jingbo Liu, Texas A&M University - Kingsville; Linda Villarreal, Texas A&M University - Kingsville*

Discussant: *Panagiotis Kosmas, University of Limassol - Cyprus*

92.063-3. Radical Youth Literacies: Black Resistance, Disability, and Liberation (Table 3). SIG-Research Focus on Black Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Activism as Resistance: The Uprising of Black Youth with Stuttering Disabilities. *Antonio L. Ellis, American University; William N. Thomas, American University; Phelton Cortez Moss, Virginia Commonwealth University; Eugene Pringle, American University*

Beyond the Mat: Centering the Literacy Experiences of Black Girls in Gymnastics through Sista Circles. *Tamara N. Moten, Wesleyan College*

Unspeakable: A Critical & Conceptual Collaboration to Unveil Black Cognitive Joy. *Karina Forsythe-Cummings, University of Michigan*

Chair: *Shawn S. Savage, University of North Carolina - Wilmington*

92.063-4. Care, Belonging, and Restoration in Academia and Education (Table 4). SIG-Research on Women and Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Caring for the Caregivers: Women Faculty and the Burnout Crisis in Teacher Preparation. *Heather K. Olson Beal, Stephen F. Austin State University; Amanda M. Rudolph, Stephen F. Austin State University; Christy Collins, Stephen F. Austin State University*

Breaking a Bitch: Styleshifting for Survival and the Mental Health Impacts of School Discipline. *Diedra W. Carlson, University of Minnesota; Aracely Thomas, University of Minnesota*

Belonging as Resistance Among Mid-Level Women of Color Administrators in Higher Education. *Rachelle Martinez, University of San Diego*

Joy, Care, and Resistance: Healing Justice Through the Labor of Immigrant Women Educators. *Jue Wang, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Lan Quach Kolano, University of North Carolina - Charlotte*

92.063-5. Voices for Change: Racial Justice, Healing, and Educational Reform (Table 5). SIG-Stress, Coping, and Resilience; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Breaking the Chains of the School-To-Prison Pipeline With Mental Health Justice. *Asianya Jones, California State University - Sacramento; Addison Duane, Sacramento State University*

It Was Just Always Like That: Staff Perspectives on Trauma-Embedded Organizational Culture. *R. Jason Lynch, Appalachian State University*

Racial Stress and Its Impact on Matterng and Affirmation Among Students of Color at PWIs. *Michael Grigsby, University of Southern California; Saba Lily Modaressi, University of Southern California*

Resilience in School During Turbulent Times: A Case in Turkiye. *Gülnur Ak Küçükçayır, Milli Eğitim Bakanlığı*
“Time to Flourish”: A Global Study on Entrepreneurial and Leadership Education in Disruptive Times. *Ianina Scheuch, TU Dresden*

92.063-6. Chinese and Confucian Perspectives (Table 6). SIG-Confucianism, Taoism, Buddhism and Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Self-Cultivation in Meditation-Based Pedagogy for Classical Chinese: Effects on Emotional Resonance, Comprehension, and Retention. *RONG DENG, The Education University of Hong Kong*

Beyond Anthropocentric Technology Ethics: A Chinese

Cosmotechanical Approach to the “Teacher Subjectivity Crisis” in the Age of AI. *Min Lin, Shenzhen University*

From the Jinshi (經世) tradition to Individuality: how Confucian ideals shaped the academic disciplines of Chinese Students in the U.S (Late Qing-Early Republican Era).

James Yang, Beijing Normal-Hong Kong Baptist University
Infusing Confucian values into teaching evaluation. *Adrian M. Blumenthal, University of Denver; Kerong Wu*

Chair: *Meixi *, University of Minnesota*

Discussant: *Ketan ., University of Massachusetts - Amherst*

92.063-7. Decolonial and Indigenous Educational Philosophies (Table 7). SIG-Caribbean and African Studies in Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Aimé Césaire’s Africana Humanism and its Educational Significance. *David T. Hansen, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Betraying the Revolution How the West and Haitian’s Elite Crushed the First Independent Black Republic. *Pierre W. Orelus, Fairfield University*

Decolonial Futures in the Caribbean: Reimagining Teacher and Leadership Education in Barbados. *Christopher Emdin, Teachers College, Columbia University; Edmund S. Adjapong, Seton Hall University*

Indigenous Pedagogies for African and Caribbean Education. *Tanya R. Manning-Lewis, Thompson Rivers University*

Chair: *Giovanni E. Whyte, University of North Dakota*

92.063-8. Queer Futurity: Chosen Families; Doing Justice, and Honoring Our Communities (Table 8). SIG-Queer Studies; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Doing Justice to Rebeca: Joteria Listening Beyond Gender Binaries and Ethnographic Legibility. *Omi Salas-SantaCruz, University of Utah; Cydney Y. Caradonna, University of Utah*

Family Chosen: Queer and Trans Reflections, Tender Moments, and Sticking With Families of Origin. *Bethy Leonardi, University of Colorado - Boulder; Nelia Peña, University of Colorado - Boulder; Keith Anthony Griffin, University of Colorado - Boulder*

Toward Gender Affirming Worlds: Imagining Ideal Education and Society with Trans, Nonbinary Youth and Caregivers. *SJ Hemmerich, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

92.063-9. Queerness, Health, and Well-Being Education: Joy, Thriving, and Imagination (Table 9). SIG-Queer Studies; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
9:45-11:15am

92.064. AERA Roundtable Session Sunday 9:45 am - Gold 4;
Roundtable Session

**92.064-1. Systems and Stories: Cultural-Historical
Perspectives on Development and Equity (Table 1).** SIG-
Cultural-Historical Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Amplification of Child Development as an Alternative to the
“Pedagogy of Poverty”: The Tale of Two Curricula. *Elena
Bodrova, Tools of the Mind, Inc; Deborah J. Leong, Tools of
the Mind, Inc; Vera Brofman, Touro College*

Contradictions in the Trauma Discourse as a Developmental
Opening. *Lara M. Beaty, LaGuardia Community College -
CUNY*

Identifying Agentic Dispositions in University–District
Partnerships: A CHAT Study of Equity-Centered Principal
Preparation. *Shweta Chandrashekhar, University of
Wisconsin - Madison; Daniella Molle, University of
Wisconsin - Madison; Arati Bapat, University of Wisconsin -
Madison; Emily Nott, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Imagining New Relations through Play: A Cultural-Historical
and Ecological Approach to Multilingual World-Making.
Edward Rivero, Teachers College, Columbia University

Nested Systems: A Cultural-Historical Activity Theory
Analysis of Special Education University Supervisory
Praxis. *Shweta Chandrashekhar, University of Wisconsin -
Madison; Thomas Owenby, University of Wisconsin -
Madison*

Chair: *Zachary R. Brown, SUNY New Paltz*

**92.064-2. Advancing Equity through Instructional Design and
Technology (Table 2).** Division I - Education in the
Professions; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Assessment Transformation in PA Education: A Cultural
Humility Framework for Bias Mitigation. *Abby Saunders,
Seton Hall University; Don Martinez, Midwestern
University; Sara Aoun, Albany Medical College; Amanda
DeVoss, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Tracy Jackson,
VIP Community Services; Ashley Tucker, PA Education
Association; Joanne Rolls, University of Utah*

A Study on the Impact of Multi-Agent-Supported 4C/ID
Learning Approach on Vocational Students' Learning
Outcomes. *Changchun Bi, East China Normal University;
Haoming Wang, East China Normal University; Yang Hong,
East China Normal University; Fanfei MENG, University of
Pennsylvania; Chunjia Bao, National University of*

Singapore; Xianlong Xu, East China Normal University
From Curriculum to Clinic: Centering Professional Identity to
Advance Equity in Medical Training. *Koya Ferrell,
University of Michigan*

Teaching to Transform: AI Simulations for Just, Reflective
Practice in Statistics Consulting Courses. *Matheus Guerrero,
California State University - Fullerton; Sunny Nguyet Le,
California State University - Fullerton*

Chair: *Tracy Boswell Fulton, University of California - San
Francisco*

**92.064-3. Applications of mixed methods research: Designs
tailored to unique contexts (Table 3).** SIG-Mixed Methods
Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Mixed-Methods Inquiry into Equitable Assessment: Data
Literacy among Culturally and Linguistically Diverse
Students. *Semi J. Yeom, Defense Language Institute*
Understanding Middle School Student Use and Prompt Patterns
with a GenAI-Based Teaching Assistant in Learning.
*Yumeng Zhu, Zhejiang University; Dan Sun, Hangzhou
Normal University; Yan Li, Zhejiang University*

Urban Teachers' Social Distance from Students and Incidents of
Classroom Violence: A Mixed Methods Study. *Ting-Yu
Ariel Chung, University of Maryland; Andrew M.
Brantlinger, University of Maryland; Elnaz Safarha,
University of Maryland; Aliya Kadirov, University of
Maryland*

Chair: *Hyun-Sook Kang, University of Illinois at Urbana-
Champaign*

**92.064-4. What is Possible: New Methodologies in Qualitative
Research (Table 4).** SIG-Qualitative Research; Roundtable
Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Decolonial Dialogic Encounters: Engaging AsianCrit as a
Research Methodology. *Robert J. Lynn, Texas Tech
University; Brendon M. Soltis, Michigan State University*
Science Fiction as Methodology: Extrapolation, Speculation,
and Fabulation in Qualitative Inquiry. *Matthew Weirick
Johnson, University of South Florida*

There's Something (More) About Bicycles: Enchantment,
Ethics, and Embodied Data. *Whitney Danielle Blaisdell,
University of Regina*

Thinking with McKittrick in Educational Inquiry. *Roya
Fathalizadeh, Arizona State University; Eric Alvarez,
Arizona State University*

Chair: *Whitney Danielle Blaisdell, University of Regina*
Discussant: *Mirka E. Koro, Arizona State University*

92.064-5. Applications of the Rasch Model in Education (Table 5). SIG-Rasch Measurement; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Measuring Impacts of a Mathematical Problem-Posing Program on Middle School Students' Mathematical Grit. *Ibrahim Burak Olmez, University of Delaware; Jinfa Cai, University of Delaware; Stephen Hwang, University of Delaware*

Psychometric Evaluation of Test Item Reading Load Scale Using the Multidimensional Rasch Model Approach. *Christopher Adah Ocheni, University of Alabama; Emmanuel Agada Onoja, University of Alabama*

Using Rasch Methodology to Identify Maximally Efficient Items from the Student Risk Screening Scale. *Christine DiStefano, University of South Carolina; Ruiqin Gao, University of South Carolina; Fred Greer, University of South Carolina; Fang Wang, University of South Carolina; Huijuan Wang, University of South Carolina*

Chair: *Abdulrasheed Olatunji Abdussalam, Visiting Prof at McGill University*

92.064-6. Confronting Oppressive Forces in Teacher

Preparation (Table 6). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

“It hinders me”: Understanding How Role Strain Shapes Clinical Experiences for Teacher Candidates of Color. *Kelly Slay, Vanderbilt University; Daniel Hay, Vanderbilt University; Aarushi Dutt, Vanderbilt University; Hope Murphy, Vanderbilt University*

Partial Progress: Antiracist Teacher Preparation in a Teacher Residency. *Annaly Rebeccah Babb-Guerra, New York University*

Preservice Teachers' Equity-Oriented Teaching Beliefs in China: The Role of Coursework and Field Experiences. *Qin Mou, KU Leuven; Orhan Agirdag, KU Leuven; Machteld Vandecandelaere, University of Leuven*

Street Data, Stronger Futures: Interrupting Colonized Teacher Preparation In Grow Your Own (GYO) Initiatives. *Eric R. Junco, Northern Illinois University*

Chair: *Kelly Slay, Vanderbilt University*

92.064-7. Black Liberatory STEM: Belonging, Wellness, and Resistance in Science Education (Table 7). SIG-Research Focus on Black Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Amplifying Voices_ The Journey To A PhD Through The Lens of Black Women in Physics. *L. Trenton S. Marsh, University of Central Florida; Camille Coffie, Spelman College; Jackie*

Chini, Ohio University; Itunu O. Ilesanmi, University of Northern Iowa

Black Liberatory Futures in STEM: Creating Spaces of Wellness, Joy, and Institutional Belonging. *Joanna N. Ali, North Carolina State University; Paula Groves Price, North Carolina A&T State University; Loydmilla dosReis, North Carolina A&T State University; Arielle King, North Carolina A&T State University; Amaya Jeffers, North Carolina A&T State University*

Examining the Role of HBCUs in the Production of STEM Graduates: A National Study. *Emiel W. Owens, Texas Southern University; Collette M. Bloom, Texas Southern University; Andrea Tyler; Holim Song, Texas Southern University; Kimberly McLeod, Abilene Christian University*
“They Don’t Value Diversity as Much as We Thought They Did”: Examining Black STEM Undergraduates’ Experiences in an Anti-DEI Climate. *Tia C. Madkins, The University of Texas at Austin; Yasmiyn Irizarry, University of Texas at Austin; Tyra Timm, University of Texas at Austin; Nkasano R. Fullerton, University of Texas at Austin; Chandell Burgess, University of Texas at Austin; Caitlin Allyne Currie, University of Texas at Austin; Juliana Okonya, University of Texas at Austin*

Chair: *Dion Tremain Harry, Oklahoma State University*

Division and SIG Posters

92.065. AERA Poster Session Sunday 9:45 am; Poster Session

92.065-1. Social, Cultural, and Emotional Foundations of Student Learning and Motivation. Division C - Learning and Instruction Cosponsored with SIG-Motivation in Education; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 9:45-11:15am

Posters:

1. The More Competent, the More Curious, and the More Interested: The Cyclical Interconnection of State-level Curiosity, Interest and Basic Psychological Needs (Poster 1). *Haoyan Huang, University of Helsinki; Yixin Zhang, Fujian Preschool Education College; Xin Tang, Shanghai Jiao Tong University*
2. Linking Competence Beliefs and Task Values in an Environmentally Relevant Science Curriculum (Poster 2). *Eva Li, University of California - Riverside; Cecilia Cheung, University of California - Riverside*
3. Adolescents' Goal Complexes Across the Transition: Profile Dynamics and Developmental Trajectories (Poster 3). *Shuyu Chen, East China Normal University; Yi Jiang, East China Normal University*
4. The Role of Socio-Emotional Skills in Academic Resilience: A Global Analysis (Poster 4). *Faming Wang, Zhejiang University; Ronnel B. King, Chinese University of Hong*

Kong

5. The Relation between Heritage Language Use and Academic Performance: PISA 2018 (Poster 5). *Yan Wu, Johns Hopkins University; Marcia H. Davis, Johns Hopkins University*
 6. What Happens After Students Receive Help? Exploring College Students' Perceptions of Receiving Academic Help (Poster 6). *Semilore F. Adelugba, Texas State University; Carlton J. Fong, Texas State University*
 7. How Do Higher Education Contexts Shape Academic Help-Seeking? A Systematic Review (Poster 7). *Molly L. Taylor, Virginia Commonwealth University*
 8. Examining the Relationships Between School Racial Climate, Racial Identity and Belonging on Black Students Motivation. (Poster 8). *Jacoby Luster, University of Michigan; Jamaal Matthews, University of Michigan*
 9. Learning to Learn: A Mixed Methods Study of Students' Metacognitive and Motivational Changes (Poster 9). *Ethan Kennedy, Lehigh University; Allison Zengilowski, Lehigh University; Brendan Alexander Schuetze, University of Utah*
 10. What Drives Math Anxiety? A Theory-Informed Machine Learning Approach to Identifying Key Predictors Among Adolescents (Poster 10). *Wondimu Ahmed, University of Akron*
 11. Making Math Meaningful: The Role of Relevance in Increasing Engagement and Achievement through Culturally-Relevant and Place-Based Digital Math Games (Poster 11). *Vanessa Wanchanit Vongkulluksn, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Monica Ceja Rodriguez, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Dulshi Nimasha Fernando, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Monika Neda, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Jacimaria Batista, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Alok Pandey, College of Southern Nevada; Daniel Sahl, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*
 12. The Power of Identity: Predicting Motivational Patterns and Outcomes in High School STEM Learning (Poster 12). *Jennie Lee, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Qingqing Zhou, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Cheryl Ann Cohen, Dept. of Educational Psychology, University of Illinois, Urbana-Champaign; Alexa Rayas, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Antonia Yuxin Hua, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Jessica R. Gladstone, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*
 13. Navigating Science Motivation: Discrimination and Socialization on Science-Embedded Achievement in Community College and University Students (Poster 13). *Albenys Diaz Hernandez, University of Michigan; Nestor Tulagan, University of Rochester*
 14. Academic Challenges and Motivation Among Asian and Asian American College Students in Computer Science (Poster 14). *Yichi Zhang, University of Georgia; Emily Quinn Rosenzweig, Teachers College, Columbia University; Harlee Robinson DiNello, University of Georgia*
 15. Measuring Working Memory in Meaningful Ways (Poster 15). *Ella Rose, University of California - Irvine; Maryam Cheraghi, University of California, Irvine; Lucia Alcalá, California State University - Fullerton; Katherine T Rhodes, University of California - Irvine; Lindsey E. Richland, University of California - Irvine*
 16. Fostering Generative Learning with Expansive Framing: A Systematic Review (Poster 16). *Daniel T. Hickey, Indiana University; Eric B. Freedman, University of Iowa; Bianca Schamberger, University of Iowa; Tripp Harris, University of South Carolina; Grant T. Chartrand, Indiana University; Morgan Qianxu Luo, Indiana University; Rebekah Jongewaard, Arizona State University*
- 92.065-2. Inquiry in the Social Contexts of Education.** Division G - Social Context of Education; Poster Session Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 9:45-11:15am
- Posters:
17. Becoming Dr Dad in the Digital Spotlight: A Multimodal Critical Discourse Analysis of PhD Influencers in China (Poster 17). *Junyi Luo, East China Normal University*
 18. Critical Social Inquiry and the Politics of Post-truth: A Matter of Trust (Poster 18). *Davis Clement, Eastern Michigan University; Michelle D. Young, University of California - Berkeley*
 19. Future Education Scenarios in 2050: Causal Layered Analysis Study through Scholars' Collective Dialogue (Poster 19). *yuanyuan zhu, Shanghai Normal University; Yuhua Bu, East China Normal University; Meng Dai, Jiangsu Second Normal University; Qing Liu, East China Normal University; Jinshen YU, Jiangnan University; GAI PINGYUN, East China Normal University; Heng Li, East China Normal University*
 20. If we tellin' the whole truth: Why community matters for Black women scholars doing Black Ph.D work (Poster 20). *Cecilia Noelle Vaughn-Guy, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Angélique Evans, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Alissa G. Irvin, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*
 21. Is College a Scam? Tik-Tok Content and Postsecondary Planning (Poster 21). *Katherine Pedersen, University of Pennsylvania; Cameron Moy, University of Pennsylvania*
 22. Laboring Bodies, Disrupted Learning: A Critical Review of Educational Marginalization of Migrant Farmworker Children in United States (Poster 22). *Oluwafisayo Grace Ajamobe, University of Ibadan; John O. Ajamobe, Texas A&M University*
 23. Narratives of Fear: The Impact Mass Deportation Policies have on Teachers and Students (Poster 23). *Theresa A. McGinnis, Hofstra; Linda Gherardi, Hofstra University*
 24. Pacing, Poetry, and Praxis: Rethinking Decolonization and Indigenization with International Students (Poster 24). *Kathleen (Kaye) Hare, University Canada West; Gitanjali Chhabra, University Canada West*
 25. Race, Geography, and Neurodivergence in Educational

- Contexts (Poster 25). *Lisa Heard, University of West Alabama; Shelly Melchior, University of West Alabama*
26. Transformative Creative Imagination: Conceptual Framework for Analyzing the Designs of Learning Experiences for Children (Poster 26). *Roni Barsoum, University of Michigan*
27. Unhomely Praxis: Palestinian Students' Agency in Israeli Jewish Schools (Poster 27). *Orwa Sedawi, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev; Assaf Meshulam, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev*
28. Using Artificial Intelligence To Detect Teacher Candidates' Funds Of Identity In Socioeconomically Diverse Urban Contexts (Poster 28). *Yan Chen, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Nick V. Flor, University of New Mexico; Moises Esteban Guitart, University of Girona*

92.065-3. Designing Preservice Teacher Learning: Exploring Lesson Planning, Computational Thinking, AR, and Generative AI. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Poster Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 9:45-11:15am

Posters:

29. Developing AI-Literacy in Pre-Service Teachers Through Lesson Planning (Poster 29). *Amelie Smucker, Radford University; Eman A. M. Amer, Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University*
30. Integrating GenAI into Lesson Planning: A Study of AI Literacy Development in EFL Teacher Education (Poster 30). *Yuze Gu, Independent Scholar; Qianqian Ma, University at Buffalo - SUNY*
31. PISA 2029 and AI Literacy: How UNESCO's Framework Can Guide Pre-Service Teacher Education (Poster 31). *Zamzami Zainuddin, Flinders University; Samuel Kai Wah Chu, Hong Kong Metropolitan University*
32. Practicing with AI Agents: Prospective Teachers' Learning to Ask Questions in Mathematics (Poster 32). *Dabae Lee, Kennesaw State University; Corey M. Webel, University of Missouri; Sheunghyun Yeo, Daegu National University of Education; Burcu Alapala, University of Missouri; Rebekah Hanak, University of Missouri*
33. Teaching with Claude: An Autoethnography on AI Collaboration and Integration in Lesson Planning (Poster 33). *Hamza Benzina, Texas A&M University; Sandra T. Acosta, Texas A&M University*

92.065-4. From Policy to Practice: Equity, Mentorship, and Transformative Learning in Preservice Teacher Education. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Poster Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 9:45-11:15am

Posters:

34. Exploring Education Legislation and Policy in Early

- Childhood Teacher Education (Poster 34). *Jolyn Blank, University of South Florida; Sophia Han, University of South Florida; Daria Smirnova, University of South Florida*
35. Linking Student Teaching and Equitable Practices: A Descriptive Study in Los Angeles (Poster 35). *Emilie Mitescu Reagan, Claremont Graduate University; Laura Vernikoff, Touro University*
36. Not Ready for Reality: Differentiated Instruction Gaps in K-12 Teacher Preparation in Secondary Schools (Poster 36). *Shiyu Dai, University of North Texas; Yishun Liu, University of Kansas*
37. Transformative Learning in Action: Shifting Prospective Primary School Teachers' Perspectives on Professional Competencies (Poster 37). *Bariş Kalender, Gaziantep University; Ayten İflazoğlu Saban, Cukurova University*
38. Wobbling Toward Meaning: A Narrative Inquiry into My Journey as an Early Childhood Teacher Educator Navigating Computing Integration (Poster 38). *Myung-jin Kim, University of Nebraska - Kearney*

92.065-5. Human and Digital Dimensions of Teacher Learning: Personality, Professional Vision, and AI Integration.

Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Poster Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 9:45-11:15am

Posters:

39. Effects of Different Video Presentations of 360°-Videos on Professional Vision and Psychological Experience in PE (Poster 39). *Swantje Brandt, Europa-Universität Flensburg; Anneke Langer, Europa-Universität Flensburg, Germany; Tim Heemsoth, Europa-Universität Flensburg*
40. From Hesitant Beginners to Confident Experts: AI Literacy among Preschool Teachers in Guangxi, China (Poster 40). *Xiya Feng, The Education University of Hong Kong; Xibei Xiong, Guangxi Normal University; Simin Cao, Shanghai Normal University; Tianhang Gao, Shanghai Normal University; Hui Li, The Education University of Hong Kong; Yukun Xu, Buffalo State - SUNY*
41. What Makes an Ideal "Teacher Personality"? Aligning InTASC Standards with the Big Five Personality Model (Poster 41). *Kevin M. Williams, Educational Testing Service; Guangming Ling, Educational Testing Service; Geoffrey Phelps, Educational Testing Service*
42. Exploring the Use of LLMs to Automatically Classify Teacher Questions in Science Classrooms (Poster 42). *Dean R. Boyle, University of Virginia; Sarah Lilly Deans, University of Virginia; Jim Bywater, James Madison University; Jennie Chiu, University of Virginia*

92.065-6. Insights on Adolescence and Youth Development: Advancement of Research and Methodological Approaches. SIG-Adolescence and Youth Development; Poster Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 9:45-11:15am

Posters:

43. Assessing the long-term impact of a self-directed learning intervention on NEET youth (Poster 43). *Kerli Kõiv, University of Tartu; Katrin Saks, University of Tartu; Pihel Hunt, University of Tartu; Annika Kuus, Rõuge Basic School*
44. Chinese Left-behind Children's Mental Health: The Role of Family Cohesion and Sense of Security (Poster 44). *Jinqian Liao, Southwest University*
45. Effect of Volunteer Motivation on Volunteer Engagement: A Moderation Model of Perceived Teacher Support (Poster 45). *Yu Kun, Fudan University; Qing Yu, Fudan University; Yangdi Han, Fudan University*
46. Exploring High School Students' Teaching Career Aspirations: A Social Cognitive Career Theory Case Study (Poster 46). *Haidée A. Jackson, University of Texas - Permian Basin; Kara Rosenblatt, The University of Texas of the Permian Basin*
47. Fosterphobia: Understanding the Marginalization of Students with Experience in Foster Care (Poster 47). *Kenyon Lee Whitman, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Blayne D. Stone, University of Pittsburgh*
48. iDrone2: Impact of an Online iDrone Camp on Students' STEM Affinity (Poster 48). *Jiyeon Yoon, University of Texas - Arlington; Jae Hyeon Ryu, University of Idaho*
49. Paternal Parenting Styles and Academic Performance in different subjects: The mediating Role of Academic self-efficacy (Poster 49). *Ruobing Wang, East China Normal University*
50. Difficult conversations: A comparative case-study of mothers' and fathers' conversations with their middle-school children (Poster 50). *Marie-Anne Suizzo, University of Texas at Austin; Jeanne Klovert, University of Texas at Austin; Ryan A. Mata, University of Minnesota*

92.066. e-Lightning Ed-Talk Session 21 - Stage 1. AERA e-Lightning Ed-Talks; AERA Ed Talk
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Exhibit Hall A - Stage 1; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- Fostering Generative Learning with Expansive Framing: A Systematic Review (Stage 1, 9:50 AM). *Daniel T. Hickey, Indiana University; Eric B. Freedman, University of Iowa; Bianca Schamberger, University of Iowa; Tripp Harris, University of South Carolina; Grant T. Chartrand, Indiana University; Morgan Qianxu Luo, Indiana University; Rebekah Jongewaard, Arizona State University*
- Adolescents' Goal Complexes Across the Transition: Profile Dynamics and Developmental Trajectories (Stage 1, 9:59 AM). *Shuyu Chen, East China Normal University; Yi Jiang, East China Normal University*
- Future Education Scenarios in 2050: Causal Layered Analysis Study through Scholars' Collective Dialogue (Stage 1, 10:08

AM). *GAI PINGYUN, East China Normal University; Yuhua Bu, East China Normal University; yuanyuan zhu, Shanghai Normal University; Heng Li, East China Normal University; Meng Dai, Jiangsu Second Normal University; Qing Liu, East China Normal University; Jinshen YU, Jiangnan University*

If we tellin' the whole truth: Why community matters for Black women scholars doing Black Ph.D work (Stage 1, 10:17 AM). *Cecilia Noelle Vaughn-Guy, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Angélique Evans, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Alissa G. Irvin, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Is College a Scam? Tik-Tok Content and Postsecondary Planning (Stage 1, 10:26 AM). *Katherine Pedersen, University of Pennsylvania; Cameron Moy, University of Pennsylvania*

Narratives of Fear: The Impact Mass Deportation Policies have on Teachers and Students (Stage 1, 10:35 AM). *Theresa A. McGinnis, Hofstra; Linda Gherardi, Hofstra University*

Pacing, Poetry, and Praxis: Rethinking Decolonization and Indigenization with International Students (Stage 1, 10:44 AM). *Kathleen (Kaye) Hare, University Canada West; Gitanjaly Chhabra, University Canada West*

Race, Geography, and Neurodivergence in Educational Contexts (Stage 1, 10:53 AM). *Lisa Heard, University of West Alabama; Shelly Melchior, University of West Alabama*

Transformative Creative Imagination: Conceptual Framework for Analyzing the Designs of Learning Experiences for Children (Stage 1, 11:02 AM). *Roni Barsoum, University of Michigan*

Chair: *Dolores Delgado Bernal, Loyola Marymount University*

92.067. e-Lightning Ed-Talk Session 21 - Stage 2. AERA e-Lightning Ed-Talks; AERA Ed Talk
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Exhibit Hall A - Stage 2; 9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Unhomely Praxis: Palestinian Students' Agency in Israeli Jewish Schools (Stage 2, 9:50 AM). *Orwa Sedawi, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev; Assaf Meshulam, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev*

Developing AI-Literacy in Pre-Service Teachers Through Lesson Planning (Stage 2, 9:59 AM). *Amelie Smucker, Radford University*

Wobbling Toward Meaning: A Narrative Inquiry into My Journey as an Early Childhood Teacher Educator Navigating Computing Integration (Stage 2, 10:08 AM). *Myung-jin Kim, University of Nebraska - Kearney*

Transformative Learning in Action: Shifting Prospective Primary School Teachers' Perspectives on Professional Competencies (Stage 2, 10:17 AM). *Barış Kalender, Gaziantep University; Ayten İflazoğlu Saban, Cukurova University*

Linking Student Teaching and Equitable Practices: A

Descriptive Study in Los Angeles (Stage 2, 10:26 AM).
Emilie Mitescu Reagan, Claremont Graduate University;
Laura Vernikoff, Touro University

Exploring the Use of LLMs to Automatically Classify Teacher
Questions in Science Classrooms (Stage 2, 10:35 AM). *Dean*
R. Boyle, University of Virginia; Sarah Lilly Deans,
University of Virginia; Jim Bywater, James Madison
University; Jennie Chiu, University of Virginia

What Makes an Ideal “Teacher Personality”? Aligning InTASC
Standards with the Big Five Personality Model (Stage 2,
10:44 AM). *Kevin M. Williams, Educational Testing Service;*
Guangming Ling, Educational Testing Service; Geoffrey
Phelps, Educational Testing Service

Difficult conversations: A comparative case-study of mothers’
and fathers’ conversations with their middle-school children
(Stage 2, 10:53 AM). *Marie-Anne Suizzo, University of*
Texas at Austin; Jeanne Klovert, University of Texas at
Austin; Ryan A. Mata, University of Minnesota

Chair: *Daphna Oyserman, University of Southern California*

Uncategorized Sessions

92.068. AERA Research in Progress Roundtable Session Five.
AERA Sessions; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
9:45-11:15am

92.068. Research-in-Progress RT009 (Sunday). Research in
Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

The Impacts of Virginia’s African American History and
Studies Courses on African American Students. *Sean Miller,*
Fairfax County Public Schools

The Remix: Hip Hop Informed Pedagogy in Grades 7-12
Classrooms. *Hyacinth T Campbell, Brock University*

The Role of Systemic Racism: How Educational Environments
and Curriculum Impact Implicit Bias. *Kiley M. Baum,*
California State University - Chico; Kevin A Click,
California State University - Chico; Lindsey Nenadal,
California State University - Chico

92.068. Research-in-Progress RT013 (Sunday). Research in
Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Faculty Decision Making and Timing of Disability
Accommodation Request. *Alexandria Cordon, California*
State University - Long Beach

Imagining Preservice Secondary Mathematics Teachers’
Approaches To Inclusivity In Future Classrooms: A

Preliminary View. *Offir Romero Castro, Western Michigan*
University

Negotiating Disclosure: Students’ Meaning-Making Around
Disability Categories In Higher Education. *MacKenzie*
Bonner, University of California - Irvine

92.068. Research-in-Progress RT020 (Sunday). Research in
Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

A Systematic Review of Generative Artificial Intelligence
(GenAI) in Preservice Teacher Education. *Wenjiao Wang,*
The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Morris Siu-Yung
Jong, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Ching Sing Chai,
Chinese University of Hong Kong

Educator Perceptions of Human-AI Co-Creativity: A Mixed
Methods Study. *Wendy Jensen, University of Denver*

Examining Future Teachers’ Connections to AI Use: Critical
Understandings about Creative Authorship. *Elizabeth Boyce,*
The University of Arizona

Generative Artificial Intelligence in Art Education: A
Systematic Literature Review of Trends and Applications.
Yihan Jiang, University of Florida; Yujiao Fan, University of
Florida

92.068. Research-in-Progress RT023 (Sunday). Research in
Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Instructor Identity in the Age of COVID: A Sociolinguistic
Study. *Sarah Sangregorio, Montclair State University*

My Managed Mind: Navigating Teacher Identity in a For-Profit
Managed Charter School. *Samantha Lopez, Florida Atlantic*
University

What Makes a Scholar? Black Women Doctoral Students’
Understanding of their Scholar Identity. *Ulili R. Emore,*
University of Texas at Austin

“Why me?” from “Mathematics Learners” to “Math Teachers”:
Identity and Pedagogical Reasoning in a Mathematics
Methods Course. *Aula Al Balad, The Ohio State University*

Constructing Educators’ Playographies: Making Meaning Out
of Teachers’ Play Experiences. *Raul Figueroa-Rivera,*
University of Illinois at Chicago

92.068. Research-in-Progress RT027 (Sunday). Research in
Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

A Review of Coherence in Mathematics Education Research:
Using an AI Tool to Support Analysis. *Madeline Keyes,*
Boston College

Evaluating the Effectiveness of the Sequential Embodied Learning Program in Geometry Learning: A Mixed-Methods Study. *Min Young Kim, Korea University; Jinha Park, Korea University; Seoyeon Choi, Korea University; Insook Han, Korea University*

Latin*-Affirming Care in Gateway Mathematics for Instructional Servingness. *Elsa Fernanda Landeros, Vanderbilt University; Luis Antonio Leyva, Vanderbilt University*

Modeling the Relationships Among Classroom Climate, Mathematics Self-concept, and Mathematics Interest. *Abel Sekone, San Diego State University*

Chair: *Ilana S. Horn, Vanderbilt University*

92.068. Research-in-Progress RT032 (Sunday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Disrupting Systemic Pushout: Examining Barriers and Supports for Latino Students at Hispanic Serving Institutions. *Fabian Pacheco, Claremont Graduate University*

Faculty and Administrators' Servingness in STEM Education at Hispanic Serving Institutions: A Systematic Review. *Eunji Ha, Korea University; Yeonwoo Lee, Korea University; Hyun Kyoung Ro, Korea University*

92.068. Research-in-Progress RT040 (Sunday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

From Conceptualization to Practice: Language Awareness in Alberta's Multilingual Classrooms. *Roula Daher, University of Calgary*

The Morale Effect: A Mixed-Method Exploration of Classroom Morale in Higher Education. *Carlos Matthews, Northern Kentucky University*

Chair: *Patricia A. Edwards, Michigan State University*

92.068. Research-in-Progress RT042 (Sunday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Evaluation As a Bridge to Foster Research-to-practice Partnerships in Nature-based Educational Programming. *Silvia Terol, Colorado State University; Jill Zarestky, Colorado State University; Sarah Walker, Colorado State University; Kaiya Tamlyn, Colorado State University; Sharde Johnson, Colorado State University; Julia Merfeld, Colorado State University; Sara LoTempio, Colorado State University; Sarah-Ashley Collins, Colorado State University*

Human-First Collaboration: Our Learnings from a Partnership

as Care Model. *Karissa D. Coady, University of Miami; Mindy Aguirre, University of Miami; Annette Mejer, University of Miami*

Impact of School-Wide Partnership on Literacy Skills in Grades K-2. *Sara White, Vanderbilt University; Carolyn Heinrich, Vanderbilt University; Thomas M. Smith, University of California - Davis*

Influence of the Teaching-Learning Process on Student Learning in an After-School Program. *Arnob Kumar Saha, University of North Texas*

Whose Voices Matter? Looking at Community Stakeholder Participation in a University-School Partnership. *Jennifer Bryson, Boston University; Cassandra Kobelski, Boston University*

Chair: *Maisie L. Gholson, University of Michigan*

92.068. Research-in-Progress RT047 (Sunday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Breathing Life into Technologies: Designing Digital Pedagogies in Oaxaca, Mexico. *Emanuel Suarez Jimenez, University of California - Santa Cruz*

Integrating Data Literacy and Storytelling in Middle School Computer Science-Infused Curriculum. *Lalita Suwattee, University of Colorado - Boulder; Srinjita Bhaduri, University of Colorado - Boulder; Jennifer K. Jacobs, University of Colorado - Boulder; Quentin Bidy, University of Colorado - Boulder; Tamara Sumner, University of Colorado - Boulder*

Building Data Literacy in Primary Education: Online Teacher Development and Professional Networks. *Mustafa Ciftcioglu, University of Edinburgh; Judy Robertson, University of Edinburgh; Serdar Abaci, University of Edinburgh*

Chair: *Louis M. Gomez, University of California - Los Angeles*

92.068. Research-in-Progress RT053 (Sunday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

Developing Academic Spanish Using Young Adult Literature and Translanguaging Pedagogies for Teacher Candidates and Students. *Wendy Mendez, National Louis University*

Exploring the Role of Pre-Service Teacher Actions in Promoting Student Engagement with Computational Thinking. *Zarina Wafula, Iowa State University; Lin Chu, Indiana University; Kristina Tank, Iowa State University; Anne Leftwich, Indiana University; Tamara Jo Moore, Purdue University*

Scaffolding Discourse Moves in Multilingual Classrooms within Mathematics Language Routines (MLRs)

Enactments. *Nurgul Isik, University of California - Santa Barbara; Sarah Ann Roberts, University of California - Santa Barbara*

92.068. Research-in-Progress RT059 (Sunday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- Inherited Silence: (Re)Discovering Cultural Identity Through Intergenerational Storytelling. *Ayanna Samuels-Francis, University of Maryland*
Racializing Cartographies: People, Schools, and Infrastructures of Race in the Bronx. *Alexandros Orphanides, Stanford University*
Environmental Racism and Educational Equity: A Working Paper on Combating Systems of Oppression. *Desirae Earmy Terrell, California State University - Dominguez Hills; Akadius Ashby, Kern High School District*

Chair: *Carolyn D. Herrington, Florida State University*

92.068. Research-in-Progress RT062 (Sunday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- Development and Validation of the Asian American Ruist Values Scale. *Ethan Yi-En Kao, University of California - Los Angeles*
"More Than a Club": Cultural Organizations in the Lives of Filipinx American College Students. *Jason M Lu, California State Polytechnic University - Pomona*
The affect, digital storytelling project, and language practice of Korean heritage language learners. *HyeEun Jung, Pennsylvania State University*
Crossing Borders, Building Belonging: Reframing Campus Climate, Mentorship, and Cultural Engagement for South Asian International Adult Learners in U.S. Higher Education. *Sharmina Akter, Texas State University*
Exploring How Highly Interactive Learning Supports Chinese Graduate Students' Early Adaptation in U.S. Education Programs. *Zichen Wang, Johns Hopkins University*

92.068. Research-in-Progress RT066 (Sunday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- Critical Practices in Teaching Film Production: Faculty Experiences. *Nicole Koschmann, Binghamton University*
A Case Study Investigating the Factors Shaping Undergraduates' Negative Attitudes Toward Calculus 1. *Cristian Florian Schreiber, Florida International University*
STEM Lecturers' Perceptions of Blended Learning in Nigerian

Universities: Emerging Insights from a Connectivist Lens. *Tomisin Damilola Fadamoro, University of Aberdeen*
Chair: *Julie M. Slayton, University of Southern California*

92.068. Research-in-Progress RT074 (Sunday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- Critical Thinking Under Siege: The Consequences of Book Banning in Public Education. *Lori Spradley, Auburn University - Montgomery; Lei Wang, Auburn University - Montgomery*
Educating high schoolers about parenting: Aligning research recommendations, parents' priorities, and state standards. *Sandra El Hadi, Harvard University; Iris Jeffries, Harvard University; Cuichun Cao, Harvard University; Meredith L. Rowe, Harvard University*
The Experiences of California Foster Youth Liaisons: Supporting Students with Experience in Foster Care. *Aurora M. Jimenez-Guerrero, Claremont Graduate University*

Chair: *Dorothy L. Espelage, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*

92.068. Research-in-Progress RT003 (Sunday). Research in Progress Roundtables; Invited Roundtable
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree Hall C;
9:45-11:15am

Participants:

- Artificial Intelligence in Surgical Medical Education: A Systematic Review in Progress. *Heba Abushanab, Utah State University; Ramy Shaaban, Utah State University*
Pushes, Pulls, and Persistence: Understanding Underrepresented Students' Trajectories in Engineering Pathways. *Amy Sarofian-Butin, Tufts University*

Chair: *Danette Waller McKinley, Foundation for Advancement of International Medical Education and Research*

Sunday, April 12th, 11:45 am

Presidential Sessions

93.010. Unforgetting Histories and Dreaming for the Future of Mathematics Education. AERA Presidential Session;
Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 404AB;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Chairs: *Megan L. Franke, University of California - Los Angeles; Maisie L. Gholson, University of Michigan*

Panelists: *Maisie L. Gholson, University of Michigan; Rochelle*

Gutierrez, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Elizabeth De Freitas, Adelphi University; Jasmine Y. Ma, New York University; Tesha Sengupta-Irving, University of California - Berkeley

AERA Sessions

93.011. 2026 AERA Annual Meeting Closing Ceremony and Transition. AERA Sessions; Invited Speaker Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 403B;
11:45am to 1:15pm
Chairs: *Tabbye M. Chavous, American Educational Research Association; Maisha T. Winn, Stanford University; Jerome E. Morris, University of Missouri - St. Louis*

Committee Sessions

93.012. How to Get the Most Out of Your Advisor Relationship. Graduate Student Council; Invited Speaker Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 402A;
11:45am to 1:15pm
Chair: *Mark Wilson, University of Houston*
Speakers: *Dave A. Louis, University of Houston; Hugo A. Garcia, University of San Diego; Mark Wilson, University of Houston*

93.013. Women's and Gender Studies Departments and the Work they do. Committee on Scholars and Advocates for Gender Equity in Education; Invited Speaker Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 501B;
11:45am to 1:15pm
Chairs: *Francesca López, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Susan Anne Cridland-Hughes, Clemson University; Shameka Nija Powell, Tufts University*
Panelists: *Laura Chavez-Moreno, University of California - Los Angeles; Marleen Villanueva, Texas Christian University; Juliann T. Anesi, Syracuse University; Amy Reid, PEN America; Marisol Lebron, University of California - Santa Cruz; Deniece Dortch, The George Washington University*

Division Sessions

93.014. Mentoring Leaders of Color: Reimagining Preparation, Support, and Leadership Pathways. Division A - Administration; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Los Feliz; 11:45am to 1:15pm
Participants:
Expanding Access to Leadership Mentorship: Reimagining

Preparation at an Urban Hispanic and Minority-Serving Institution. *Lizette Navarrete-Burks, University of Northern Colorado*

“Halting the Churn and Burn”: Improving Principal Support Structures for Leaders of Challenged Schools. *Reginald D. Wilkerson, College of William & Mary*

Preparation to Practice: Re-examining Principal Learning and Leadership in Times of Complexity. *Paul Campbell, The University of Hong Kong*

Propping the Door Open for Others – Mentoring While Black and Male: Developing the Gordon Paradigm of Mentorship of Leaders. *Phillip A Smith, Fordham University; Wesley J Morris, Southern Vision Alliance*

Chair: *Natasha N. Johnson, Augusta University*

Discussant: *Jamon H. Flowers, University of Georgia*

93.015. Queer Resistance, Detracking & Racelighting: A Historical Case of an Urban Mountain-West High School. Division A - Administration; Symposium
Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Los Cerritos; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Archival Foundations: Detracking in Context. *Katie Nitka, Salt Lake City School District*

Racelighting Counterstories in Practice. *Nicole C. Wilson Steffes, University of Utah & Westminster University*

Queer Resistance and School Improvement. *Sonny Partola, University of Wisconsin - Stevens Point*

Leadership Pathways for Inclusive Detracking. *Laura Cheney, University of Utah*

Chair: *Nicole C. Wilson Steffes, University of Utah & Westminster University*

Discussant: *Laurence Parker, University of Utah*

93.016. Educating for Sovereignty: A K-12 Recovery Framework for Indigenous and Latinx Students. Division B - Curriculum Studies; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304A;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

The Implications of K-12 Recovery Work for Public Education in the Twentieth Century. *Elena Vicentita Valdez, New Mexico Highlands University*

Exploring the Definitions of Intercultural Education for the Borderlands. *Minea Armijo Romero, New Mexico State University*

La Trenz Curricular: Spanish Language Arts as Decolonial Praxis in Dual Language Secondary Education. *Mishelle Jurado, University of New Mexico*

Chair: *Minea Armijo Romero, New Mexico State University*

Discussant: *Carlos A. LopezLeiva, University of New Mexico*

93.017. Islamic Epistemologies, Decolonial Pedagogy, and Many Ways of Knowing. Division B - Curriculum Studies;

Symposium

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304B;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Toward an Integrative Islamic Philosophy of Education:
Ghazzali, Hayy ibn Yaqzan, and the Ethics of Knowing.

Arshad Imtiaz Ali, The George Washington University

Pedagogical Possibilities of Muslim Science Epistemologies
and Storywork Curriculum. *Ebtissam Oraby, The George
Washington University*

A Multimodal (and Ghazalian) Analysis of Epistemic
Openness in a Storywork Based Elementary Science
Classroom. *Samuel Burmester, University of California -
Santa Cruz*

Chair: *Ananda M. Marin, University of California - Los Angeles*

Discussant: *Ananda M. Marin, University of California - Los
Angeles*

**93.018. AI in Higher Education: Balancing Support, Ethics,
and Agency.** Division C - Learning and Instruction; Paper
Session

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, San Gabriel A; 11:45am
to 1:15pm

Participants:

A Crutch or Catalyst? AI Locus of Control and Proactive Skill
Development. *Xiaofei Lyu, Tsinghua University; Chanchan
Liu, Tsinghua University; Jun Wei, Tsinghua University*

Ethics, Use, and The Future: Three Years of Longitudinal Data
on GenAI in Higher Education. *Luke Parker, Australian
Catholic University; Josh Hayes, University of Kansas; Jane
A. Loper, University of Kansas; Christopher Carter,
University of Kansas; Alice L. Karakas, Washburn
University*

Assessment in the AI Era: Cultivating Critical Thinking
through Socratic Questioning and Intellectual Standards.
Fatiha Bazouche, Ohio University

Enhancing ESL/EFL Writing Through GenAI-SRL instruction:
Effects on Self-Regulated Learning, Cognitive Processing,
and Writing Performance. *Jing Wang, Zhejiang University;
Tianni Chen, Zhejiang University; Yuqin Yang, Central
China Normal University*

From Feedback to Uptake: EFL Students' Perception and Use
of ChatGPT Across Writing Stages. *Jiyoon Jung, Korea
University; Sewon Joo, Florida State University; Insook
Han, Korea University*

**93.019. Toward a National Infrastructure for Equitable, AI-
Enhanced Learning Diagnostics in STEM Education.**

Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies;
Symposium

InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 7th Floor,
Hollywood Ballroom I; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Optimizing Cognitive Diagnosis CAT: Addressing Practical

Challenges through Psychometric Innovation. *Jing Huang,
Purdue University; Yuxiao Zhang, Purdue University; Xiyu
Wang, Purdue University; Hua-Hua Chang, Purdue
University*

Cognitive Diagnostics for Calculus and Mechanics. *Jayson
Nissen, Montana State University; Kevin Roberge; Ben Van
Dusen, Iowa State University*

An AI-Driven Expert Framework for Instructional Content
Recommendation via Adaptive Testing within Intelligent
Learning Systems. *Amirezza Mehrabi, Purdue University;
Jason W Morphew, Purdue University*

Envisioning LASSO as National Infrastructure: Scaling
Cognitive Diagnostics and Unlocking Equitable Learning
Data. *Ben Van Dusen, Iowa State University; Jayson Nissen,
Montana State University; Jason W Morphew, Purdue
University*

Exploring the Role of CD-CAT in Gateway STEM Learning
with Generative AI. *Hua-Hua Chang, Purdue University*

Chair: *Hua-Hua Chang, Purdue University*

Discussant: *Odis Johnson, Johns Hopkins University*

**93.020. Centering Cultural Wealth and Student Voice in
College Readiness.** Division E - Counseling and Human
Development; Symposium

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 309;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Cultural Resources and College Readiness: Youth Participatory
Research with First-Generation Students. *Robert Richard
Martinez, William & Mary; Katherine Barko-Alva, College
of William & Mary*

Leveraging Cultural Wealth in Comprehensive School
Counseling: Supporting College Readiness and Mental
Wellness. *Robert Richard Martinez, William & Mary;
Pamela Harris, William & Mary Law School*

School Counselor Support on FAFSA Completion: The
Intersection of Rurality and First-Generation College Status.
Cathy Longstreet, San Diego State University

Understanding BIPOC Student Experiences in Advanced
Placement Coursework. *Lillian Martz, Portland State
University; Maritza Azucena Salazar Cha, University of La
Verne*

Chair: *Laura Owen, San Diego State University*

Discussant: *Laura Owen, San Diego State University*

**93.021. Centering Marginalized Voices in the History of
Higher Education.** Division F - Historical Inquiry in
Education; Paper Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 306A;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Reframing Higher Education Concepts in China: From
Epistemic Dependency to Localization through a Triple-
Layer Framework. *Jiahui Li, Guangzhou University; Hui*

Liu, Guangzhou University; Yuyang Yan, Guangzhou University; Guang Hui Wang, Guangdong Polytechnic Normal University

"Providing opportunity for closer acquaintance": The Social Lives of Faculty Wives Organizations. *Deirdre Mayer Dougherty, Knox College*

St. Artemisia Bowden: Black Women's Place in Texas' Historically Black Community College Context. *Chaddrick James-Galloway, Texas A&M University; Francena F.L. Turner, National Park Service; Jeremy Bohonos, Texas State University; ArCasia D. James-Galloway, Texas A&M University*

How Student Values Uphold or Reconstruct Institutional Ones: A Critical Analysis of University Marketing Materials During the Era of Affirmative Action. *Cydney Ava Socias, Smith College; Shannon Audley, Smith College*

Chair: *Lindsay Byron, University of Florida*

Discussant: *Amal Kumar, California State University - Sacramento*

93.022. Black Youth Ingenuity as Disruption Towards Bright and Just Futures. Division G - Social Context of Education; Symposium

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 301A; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Black Child Emotionality: An Exploration into the Affective Lives of 20 Black Children. *Demond Hill, University of Chicago*

The Art To Surrender: Creatively Writing about Black Girl Life. *Kenly Brown, Spencer Foundation*

Nowhere to be Found: Young, Black, Queer, and Disturbed- A Systematic Literature Review. *Jocardo E Ralston, University of Pennsylvania*

Black Boys Make Dreams of Love Come True. *Aukeem A. Ballard, University of California - Berkeley*

Chair: *Ed Brockenbrough, University of Pennsylvania*

Discussant: *Yolanda Sealey-Ruiz, Teachers College, Columbia University*

93.023. Navigating Identity and Political Context in Higher Education Settings. Division G - Social Context of Education; Paper Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 303A; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Challenging the Elite Imaginary: Chinese Students' Precarious Labour, Symbolic Agency, and Identity Negotiation in UK Higher Education. *Junzhe Gu, University of Cambridge*

Constrained Inclusion Within Campus Environments: The Experiences of Undocumented College Students in California and Texas. *Jerusalem Davila, University of California - Los Angeles; Cinthya Salazar, University of California - Los Angeles; Diego Castro Gomez, University*

of California - Los Angeles

Deconstructing "True-Engineer" Stereotypes: Experiences of a Neurodivergent Female Student's Sense of Belonging in Engineering. *Karla Mariana Escobar, University of Texas - San Antonio; Sidury Christiansen, University of Texas - San Antonio*

International Graduate Students' Experiences with DEI Programs at a U.S. University: A Study on Adaptation and Predisposition. *Hongwei Yang, University of West Florida; Jian Su, The University of Tennessee - Knoxville; Edward Okai-Boafo, University of West Florida; Kwame Owusu Daaku, University of West Florida*

Navigating Higher Education: How AI Supports Special Education Students in College Applications in Texas. *Han Bum Lee, University of Texas - San Antonio; John L. Davis, University of Texas San Antonio; Sharon L. Nichols, University of Texas - San Antonio; Jasmine Victor, University of Texas - San Antonio*

Chair: *Jerusalem Davila, University of California - Los Angeles*

Discussant: *Emma Miriam Lezberg, Harvard University*

93.024. AI, Assessment, and Leadership: Reimagining Educational Practice in the GenAI Era. Division H - Research, Evaluation and Assessment in Schools; Paper Session

InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Hancock Park West; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Expert Perspectives on AI Literacy for K-12 with an Emphasis on Assessment. *Teresa M. Ober, Educational Testing Service; Caitlin Tenison, ETS; Tenaha P. O'Reilly, Educational Testing Service; Beata Beigman Kelbanov, Educational Testing Service; Jesse R. Sparks, Educational Testing Service; Diego Zapata-Rivera, ETS*

More than a feeling: How AI policy and educator sentiment affect AI allowance on assessment. *Abby Holm, Pearson Educational Measurement; Muireann Hendriksen, Pearson Education, Inc.; Lara N. Southard, Pearson Education, Inc.; Jessica Yarbrow, Pearson Education, Inc.; Emily R. Lai, Pearson*

Construction of Principal's Leadership Model and Assessment Tool in Generative Artificial Intelligence Era. *Lingling Gong, East China Normal University; Shuzhen Yu, East China Normal University*

Multi-agent Large Language Model systems for Analyzing Elementary Students' Constructed Response. *Xunlei Qian, Michigan State University; Namsoo Shin, Michigan State University; Harvey Li, Michigan State University; Yucheng Chu, Michigan State University; Cory S. Miller, Michigan State University; Joseph S. Krajcik, Michigan State University; Jiliang Tang, Michigan State University; Yue Xing, Michigan State University*

Harnessing GenAI for Automated Essay Scoring: A Multi-Agent Architecture for Large-Scale Writing Assessment. *Jun*

Qian, East China Normal University; Jing Leng, East China Normal University; Siyu Wang, East China Normal University

Chair: *Teresa M. Ober, Educational Testing Service*

93.025. Advancing Competency-Based Assessment: Evidence-Based Decisions. Division I - Education in the Professions; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Plaza II;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Competency-Based Assessment: What Are We Measuring? *Ara Tekian, University of Illinois at Chicago*

Defining Competence: The Interplay of Legal Education, Accreditation, and Licensure. *Jason Scott, AccessLex institute; Andrea Pals, AccessLex Institute*

Not Just Graduated, but Competent: Reframing Readiness for Physical Therapist Clinical Practice. *Jean Ann Fitzpatrick, Columbia University; Gail M. Jensen, Creighton University; Steven Chesbro, American Physical Therapy Association; Huiju Carrie Chen, Kaiser Permanente Bernard J. Tyson School of Medicine*

Validating ECFMG Certification Policy Changes Using ACGME Milestones. *Shiyao Yuan, FAIMER, a Division of Intealth; Kenji Yamazaki, Accreditation Council for Graduate Medical Education*

Defining Competence: Assessment Strategies in Aligning Different Frameworks in One Medical School. *Xiaomei Song, Case Western Reserve University*

Chair: *Danette Waller McKinley, Foundation for Advancement of International Medical Education and Research*

Discussant: *Stan Hamstra, University of Toronto*

93.026. Access to and Equity in Canadian Higher Education for Mature Students Symposium. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum F;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Reflections on Black Student Access Initiatives at Canadian Universities During the War on "Woke" Higher Education. *Vidal Chavannes, University of Toronto*

Understanding Sociocultural Factors of Black Queer Mature Students' Transitions to Higher Education. *Lance Trevor McCready, University of Toronto - OISE*

Opening Doors: STEM Education Opportunities for Mature Students in Postsecondary Education. *Nadia Qureshi, University of Toronto - OISE*

CBE: Critically Building Educational Alternatives to Competency-Based Education for Adult Learners. *Paula Veronica Elias, University of Toronto*

Mapping Carceral Education Programs for Mature Students in Ontario: A Case for Collective Learning. *Dargine Rajeswaran, University of Toronto - OISE*

Chair: *Lance Trevor McCready, University of Toronto - OISE*
Discussant: *Maira Tavares Mendes, University of Toronto - OISE*

93.027. We Demand More: Expanding our Frames and Approaches to Serve the Needs of OUR Community. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum H;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Brokering Change: Examining Institutional Responses and Co-optation of Black Student Demands in Higher Education Organizations. *Emerald Green, University of California - Berkeley*

Rural-Serving Community Colleges and the Democratic Mission in California's San Joaquin Valley. *Mayra Nuñez Martinez, University of California - Davis; Arlyn Y. Moreno Luna, University of California - Los Angeles; Mayra Puente, University of California - Santa Barbara; Daniel Rios Arroyo, Appalachian State University; Marlene Lopez Torres, University of California - Santa Barbara*

Serving on their own terms: Challenging dominant HSI narratives through a Puerto Rican HSI perspective. *Lauren M. Shook, University of Texas - El Paso; Edwin J. Perez, University of Texas - El Paso; Anne-Marie Nunez, University of Texas - El Paso*

Sisterhood While Black in Austerity Academy: Sister Circles as Praxis, Method, and Opportunity to Belong. *Jada A. Phelps, Michigan State University; Briana Green, Michigan State University*

Discussant: *Jordan N. Harper, Morgan State University*

93.028. From Certification to Retention: How Pathways and Supports Shape the Teaching Workforce (US, China, and Chile). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Atrium II;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Performance Predictors on a Teacher Licensure Exam:

Exploring Scores from a Foundations of Reading Test.

Beverly J. Trezek, University of Wisconsin - Madison;

Kimber L. Wilkerson, University of Wisconsin - Madison

Teacher Certification Pathways and Long-Term Teacher Retention: A 10-Year Longitudinal Analysis. *Janet Solis Rodriguez, University of Texas - San Antonio; Pedro Reyes, University of Texas at Austin*

Teacher Pathways Research-Practice Partnership (RPP) in Arizona and Utah. *Reino Makkonen, WestEd; Alicia J. Wyche Okpareke, WestEd*

The Impact of The Teacher Qualification Examination Reform on the College Admission of Teaching-track Students. *Yuxuan Qin, Fudan University; Peikang Zhang, Fudan University*

Who Stays, Who Leaves? Teacher Turnover And Policy

Changes Among Chilean Schools (2007–2024). *Alessandra Diaz-Sacco, Universidad de los Andes Chile; Dany Lopez-Gonzalez, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile; Macarena Salas, Universidad San Sebastian; Diego Carrasco, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile; Jose-Ignacio Calderon, Universidad de Chile*

Chair: *Jing Su, University of California - Santa Barbara*

Discussant: *Susan Kemper Patrick, Learning Policy Institute*

93.029. Implementing Ethnic Studies in Bay Area Schools: Research on Teachers, Pedagogy, and Curriculum.

Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 6;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

The Evolving Pedagogies of Novice Ethnic Studies Teachers.
Kevin Anderson, Stanford University; Irene Castillon, Stanford University

Developing Pedagogical Toolkits in Support of the Ethnic Studies Mandate. *Jason Muniz, University of California - Berkeley*

Coaching for Liberation: Collaborating with a First-Year English Teacher to Integrate Ethnic Studies. *Stephanie Robillard, St. Mary's College of California*

Chair: *Stephanie Robillard, St. Mary's College of California*

Discussant: *Stephanie Robillard, St. Mary's College of California*

93.030. Teachers of Color Learning, Resisting, and Designing for Equitable Futures. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Symposium

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 7;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Designing for Cross-Geographic Solidarities: Teachers of Color Convening to Imagine Possible Futures. *Danny C. Martinez, University of California - Davis; P. Zitali Morales, University of Illinois at Chicago; Ramon Antonio Martinez, Stanford University*

Exploring "Brotherhood" as a Support for Black and Brown Male Teacher Candidates. *Ceily Moore, University of Illinois at Chicago; Jeniece M. Fleming, University of Illinois at Chicago; Decoteau J. Irby, University of Illinois at Chicago*

Navigating the Strategic Terrain: Asian American Teachers' Everyday Tactics for Futuring K-12 Asian American Studies. *Jennifer Higgs, University of California - Davis; Esther June Kim, College of William & Mary; Noreen Naseem Rodriguez, Michigan State University; Sohyun An, Kennesaw State University; Michael Brown, University of Michigan*

Examining the Translingual Pedagogies of Resistance of Mayan Teachers in Yucatán. *Monica Gonzalez Ybarra, University of Illinois; Marisol Jimenez, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Blanca Bustos, University of Illinois at*

Urbana-Champaign; Monica Celeste Sanchez, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign

Imagining Liberatory Futures: Pivotal Moments in the Making of Justice-Oriented Teachers of Color. *Alexis Patterson Williams, University of California - Davis; Téa Skye Pusey, University of California - Davis; Christopher Jadallah, University of California - Los Angeles*

Chair: *Elizabeth Castro, Central Washington University*

Discussant: *Betina Hsieh, University of Washington*

93.031. Parental Choice, Marketing, and the Challenge of Equity in School Choice Contexts. Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 10; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Rating the Raters: Markets, Isomorphism, and Information Asymmetry. *Christopher A. Lubienski, Indiana University; Steffi E. Thomas, Indiana University; Kristin Schumacher, Indiana University*

"Where You Belong?": Ease and Privilege in Choosing the Local Public School in Copenhagen. *Molly V. Makris, Guttman Community College - CUNY; Allison Roda, Molloy University; Mira C. Debs, Yale University; Rikke Skovgaard Nielsen, Aalborg University*

Finding a Virtue in Algorithmic Systems: Parent Perspectives on School Enrollment Lotteries. *Andrew Kissel, Old Dominion University; Jason Saltmarsh, Old Dominion University; Jackie Nikiema, Old Dominion University*
Shaping Choices: Exploring School Marketing Under Open Enrollment. *Terri S. Wilson, University of Colorado - Boulder*

Chair: *Linn E. Posey-Maddox, Temple University*

Discussant: *Amanda U. Potterton, University of Kentucky*

SIG Sessions

93.032. Varieties of Arts-Integrated Learning Experiences.

SIG-Arts and Learning; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 1;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

"Part of My Identity, But Not Something I Did": Arts Integration in Music and Dance as a Bridge to Cultural Connection. *Katherine Espinoza-Talati, Trinity University; Melissa A. Garza, Texas A&M University - San Antonio*
Activism in Action: Preparing Elementary Pre-Service Teachers to Teach Critically through Arts Integration. *Abigail Stebbins, The Ohio State University; John Samuels, Kennesaw State University*

Changing Education Through the Arts (CETA) National Pilot Program: Teacher Professional Development in Arts Integration. *Reba Troxler, John F Kennedy Center for the*

Performing Arts; Annie Begle, John F. Kennedy Center for the Performing Arts; Stephanie McKeel, The John F. Kennedy Center for the Performing Arts; Muna J. Shami, John F. Kennedy Center for the Performing Arts

A Systematic Review of Arts Integration in Elementary STEAM Education. *Jiyoon Kang, The Ohio State University; Bosun Min, Korea National University of Education*

The Impact of Arts-Integration Professional Learning on Teacher Practice and Student Outcomes. *Azadeh Hassani, University of Nebraska - Lincoln; Guy Trainin, University of Nebraska - Lincoln; HyeonJin Yoon, University of Nebraska - Lincoln; Kimberley D'Adamo, University of Nebraska - Lincoln*

Chair: *William Zhou, The George Washington University*

Discussant: *Maggie Broderick, National University*

93.033. Not all Bilingual Education Policies are the Same:

Learning from History to Build the Future. SIG-Bilingual Education Research; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 501C;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

From ESL to Dual Language Model: Skipping Bilingual Education. *Trish Morita-Mullaney, Purdue University*
Unforgetting Language Legacies, Imagining Equitable Futures: Re-visioning Dual-Language Education in Massachusetts. *Elenita Irizarry Ramos, Massachusetts Department of Elementary and Secondary Education*

Dual/Heritage Language Programs are the Law: Grant Funded Initiatives and Opportunities to Enact Asset-based Practices for Multilingual Students in Washington. *Patricia E. Venegas-Weber, University of Washington; Kristin Percy-Calaff, Office of Superintendent of Public Instruction, Washington*

Under the Law: Unveiling Ideological Orientations and Local Practices of Bilingual-Bicultural Education Programs in Wisconsin. *Cory Mathieu, Western Washington University; Mariana Castro, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Kathryn Henn Reinke, University of Wisconsin - Oshkosh; Zach Page, University of Wisconsin - Green Bay*

Chair: *Caroline E. Parker, Wisconsin Center for Educational Research*

Discussant: *Kate Menken, Queens College - CUNY*

93.034. Osoyua and Umoja - Bridging Borders, Building Futures: Decolonized Virtual and Hybrid Collaborations for Global Learning and Faculty-Student Engagement.

SIG-Caribbean and African Studies in Education;
Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum B; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Afro-Diasporic Centered Internationalization: Blending Research and Practice. *Dawn Michele Whitehead, American*

Association of Colleges and Universities

Globalizing Inclusive Education Policy: Bridging Theory and Practice in Higher Education. *Charity Muraguri, United States International University - Africa*

Reclaiming the Global Curriculum: Local Innovation in Technology Education from Low and Middle Income Countries. *Leah Mutanu, United States International University - Africa; Joyce Muchemi, United States International University - Africa; Timothy Okech, United States International University - Africa*

Prompting Without Borders: Equitable AI Co-Creation Between Kenyan and U.S. Learners. *Kenley Obas, Alabama State University*

Chair: *Denise Davis-Maye, Alabama State University*

Discussant: *Tamara Bertrand Jones, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

93.035. Curriculum, Contexts, and Considerations:

Homeschool Research Breaking New Ground. SIG-Charters & School Choice; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum A; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Linguistic Diversity in California Homeschooling. *Georgina Justice Aubin, USF*

Self-Regulated Learning and Self-Efficacy among Homeschooled Students: A Systematic Review. *Xue Wang, Johns Hopkins University; Genevieve Smith, Johns Hopkins University; Angela R. Watson, Johns Hopkins University*
Structured and Unstructured Homeschooling: Another Proposal for Broadening the Taxonomy. *Andrea Honeycutt, University of Arkansas at Fayetteville; Albert Cheng, University of Arkansas at Fayetteville*

What Drives Homeschool Participation: A Multisource and Multistate Examination. *Angela R. Watson, Johns Hopkins University; Alanna V. Bjorklund-Young, Johns Hopkins University; Genevieve Smith, Johns Hopkins University*

Public Education Resources for Homeschoolers in North Carolina. *Christy Batts, North Carolina State University*

Chair: *Robert A. Maranto, University of Arkansas*

Discussants: *Timberly L. Baker, Arkansas State University; Sam Naab, University of Oklahoma*

93.036. Co-Designing Futures: Latina Scholars Build the East Coast RAC Through Collective Vision and Shared Praxis.

SIG-Critical Educators for Social Justice;
Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304C;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Spatial Belonging and Collective Imagination: Reflections on a West Coast RAC Site Visit. *Cristina M. Medellin, Bank Street College of Education; Vanessa Rodriguez, New York University; Alexandra Figueras-Daniel, National Institute*

for Early Education Research

Envisioning an East Coast RAC Planning Retreat at a Midwest Institution. *Mariana Souto-Manning, Erikson Institute; Maxine McKinney de Royston, Erikson Institute*

Formando Comunidad: Convivencia and the Future of East Coast Latina Research Spaces. *Lindsay Pérez Huber, California State University - Long Beach; Maria C. Malagon, California State University - Fullerton; Verónica Nelly Vélez, Western Washington University*

Chair: *Daniel Gilbert Solorzano, University of California - Los Angeles*

Discussant: *Dolores Delgado Bernal, Loyola Marymount University*

93.037. The Power Of (Un)Forgetting, Historical Consciousness And Decolonial Future Of Education. SIG-Decolonial, Postcolonial, and Anti-Colonial Studies in Education; Paper Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 303B;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Persons Concern: Unforgetting Coloniality and Imagining Futures in Refugee Education. *Adnan Turan, Arizona State University*

Transpacific Formations of Asian American Education: Unforgetting Cold War Empire and Reenvisioning Relational Methodologies. *Sun Young Lee, Wichita State University*

Unforgetting Censorship, Reimagining Academic Freedom: The Suppression of Discourse Around Palestine in U.S. Education. *Mai Zaru, Southern Methodist University; Danfeng Soto-Vigil Koon, University of San Francisco; Huriya Jabbar, University of Southern California*

Decolonial Praxis in an Era of Constraint: Faculty Reflection, Refusal, and the Reimagining of Pedagogy. *Bianca J. Nightengale-Lee, Western Michigan University; Michelle Vaughan-McGovern, Florida Atlantic University; Paul Massy, Florida Memorial University; Bryan H. Nichols, Florida Atlantic University; Daniella Orias, Florida Atlantic University; Regis Fox, Florida Atlantic University*

An Autoethnographic Kinning Case Study of Participatory Violence and Fugitive Convivial Praxis in the University. *Sahar D. Sattarzadeh, Nelson Mandela University; Charlie Parker, University of Colorado - Denver; Daranee Taychachaiwongse Teng, University of Colorado - Denver*

Chair: *Michael Joseph, Texas Tech University*

Discussant: *M. Nathan Tanner, University of Nevada - Reno*

93.038. Workforce Wellbeing and Retention in Early Childhood Education. SIG-Early Education and Child Development; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Georgia I;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Examining the Role of EHS-CCP in the Early Childhood Workforce: Identifying Work Supports Associated with Lower Turnover Rates. *Cynthia I. Palomino, E3 Alliance; Brittany Alexander, Arizona State University; Eric Bucher, Arizona State University*

Cumulative Child Risk and Early Childhood Teacher Job Commitment: The Mediating Roles of Depression and Exhaustion. *Weiyi Cheng, University of Oklahoma; Kyong-Ah Kwon, University of Oklahoma*

Toward an Expanded Conceptual Model of Early Childcare and Education Quality: A Computational Analysis of 53 Years of Research. *Yan Jiang, Stanford University*

“I Love Teaching but I must Quit”: A Systematic Review on Early Childhood Teacher Turnover. *Xin Li, University of Houston; Dandan Liang, University of Houston; Huang Wu, University of Missouri - Kansas City; Isaac Awortwe, University of Texas at Austin; Salenah Cartier, University of Houston*

Chair: *Cynthia I. Palomino, E3 Alliance*

Discussant: *Jennifer Jo Baumgartner, Louisiana State University*

93.039. Hip Hop in the Margins: Hip Hop, Comics, and Critical Speculative Pedagogies. SIG-Hip Hop Theories, Praxis & Pedagogies; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum J;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Moon Girl Magic: Black Youth Art and Musical Motivations via Graphic Novels and Pop Culture. *Christian M. Hines, Texas State University*

“Nah, Imma do my own thing”: Performing Remix Pedagogy Grounded in Hip-Hop Culture and Black Feminist Thought. *Sasha Sanders, California Polytechnic State University - San Luis Obispo*

Visual Sankofarration: Speculative Visual Literacies and the Pedagogy of Hip Hop Histories. *Walter Greason, Macalester College*

Paint, Panels, and Possibilities: Graffiti, Comics, and Critical Multimodal Literacies in Educational Research. *Michael B. Dando, St. Cloud State University*

Rhymes, Resistance, and the Rise of the Superhero in the Classroom: A Critical Pedagogical Vision for DEI. *Mike Nguyen, Franklin W. Olin College of Engineering*

Chair: *Wayne Au, University of Washington - Bothell*

Discussant: *Tasha Iglesias, Utah State University*

93.040. Cognitivism and Classrooms in the Learning Sciences. SIG-Learning Sciences; Paper Session
Westin Bonaventure, Level 2, Echo Park; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

“Hold on, I Want to Think More”: Mapping Epistemic Affect and Identity Through Multimodal Engagement in Reasoning Tasks. *Mahsa Rahmati Masouleh, Iowa Department of*

Education; Matthew E. Lira, University of Iowa
Game Design Learning Context as an Implicit Prompt for Metacognitive Development. *Rebekah Snyder, University of Missouri*

Infants on the move: 3D spatial cameras as a tool for designing classrooms and curriculum. *Amanda Reeves Fellner, Teachers College, Columbia University; Mako Miura, Teachers College, Columbia University; Tran Templeton, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Teacher–Student Cognitive Interaction and Inter-brain Coupling in Authentic Classrooms. *Xiaomeng Xu, Tsinghua University; Yu Zhang, Tsinghua University*

Chair: *Dalila Dragnic-Cindric, Digital Promise*

93.041. Innovative Mixed Methods Research Practices in Mathematics Education Contexts. SIG-Mixed Methods Research Cosponsored with SIG-Research in Mathematics Education; Symposium
InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, K-Town; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Quantizing and Visualizing the Influence of Scaffolding Moves on Mathematical Modeling Competencies. *Jennifer Czoher, Texas State University; Alexander White, Texas State University-San Marcos; Sindura Kularajan, Utah State University; Elizabeth Anne Roan, Texas State University; Andrew Baas, Texas State University*

Utilizing Annotated Digital Timelining in Mathematics Education Research: Exploring Elementary School Teachers' Culturally Relevant Competencies and Finch Robot Orchestrations. *Marcus Yuen-Yiu Cheung, Teachers College, Columbia University; Chamarra Alicia Ophelia Coward, Teachers College, Columbia University; Irina Lyublinkaya, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Going Beyond the Numbers: An Explanatory Sequential Mixed Methods Study in Postsecondary Mathematics. *Molly Christine Bowen, Baylor University*

Fostering Community through Contemplative Pedagogy: The Case of a Mandatory Post-Secondary Mathematics Course. *Leslie P. Shayer, Okanagan College*

A Case of Crossover Mixed Analyses in Mathematics Education Research. *Heather Lynn Johnson, University of Colorado - Denver; Courtney Donovan, University of Colorado - Denver; Evan McClintock, University of Colorado - Denver*

Chairs: *Trena L. Wilkerson, Baylor University; Julie Herron, Air Force Academy; Michelle L. Peters, University of Houston - Clear Lake*

Discussant: *Emma P. Bullock, Sam Houston State University*

93.042. From Idea to Impact: Candid Reflections on Building Interventions. SIG-Motivation in Education; Symposium
Westin Bonaventure, Level 3, Avalon; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Trials, Errors, and Tiny Wins: What We Learned from Developing a Peer Mindset Intervention. *Eunjin Seo, Texas State University; So Yeon Lee, The University of Alabama at Birmingham*

Design and Development of Math Confidence Intervention: Insights from Reflective Practice. *Hyun Ji Lee, Hunter College, The City University of New York; Sungwha Kim, Korea University - Brain and Motivation Research Institute; Mimi Bong, Korea University*

Catalyzing an Orientation for Agency: The Development of an Intervention to Support Active Motivation. *Erika A. Patall, University of Southern California; Amanda Vite, University of Southern California; Jeanette Zambrano, California State University - San Bernardino; Alana Aiko Uilani Kennedy, Northern Arizona University; Nicole M. Yates, University of Southern California; Germine Awad, University of Michigan; Carlton J. Fong, Texas State University; Keenan Pituch, Arizona State University; Yanyan Zong, University of Southern California; Pedram Zarei, Texas State University; Lillian Nguyen, University of Michigan; Diane Lee, University of Southern California; Christa Bancroft, University of Southern California; Kristy Daniel, Texas State University - San Marcos; Timothy A. McKay, University of Michigan; Stephen J. Aguilar, University of Southern California; Kevin O'Neal Cokley, University of Michigan; Joseph Vallin, University of Southern California; Carolyn Jess, Texas State University; Cassidy L. Martin, University of Southern California*

From Theory to Practice: The “Messy” Realities of a Communal Relevance Intervention in STEM Classrooms. *DeLeon Gray, North Carolina State University; Tamika L. McElveen, Miami University (OH); Briana Green, Michigan State University; Lauren H. Bryant, North Carolina State University*

Chairs: *So Yeon Lee, The University of Alabama at Birmingham; Eunjin Seo, Texas State University; Cameron Hecht, University of Rochester*

Discussant: *Cameron Hecht, University of Rochester*

93.043. Critiquing Histories and Imagining New Futures for Music Education. SIG-Music Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Georgia II; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Alumni Experiences of Diversity and Community Engagement in Postsecondary Music Curricula. *Christian Michael Folk, University of Texas at Austin; Angie L. Miller, Indiana University*

Music Teacher Experiences & Expressions of Agency in a Professional Development Study Group on Trauma-Informed Approaches. *Amy Sierzega, University of New Hampshire*

Through Funk and Foolishness: Centering Queer Black Youth's Resistance, Healing, and Futurity in Music Education.

Lorenzo Sánchez-Gatt, Boston University

Why Creativity?: Historicizing the Construction of Creativity and Otherness in Music Education. *Noah Karvelis, Northern Arizona University*

Chair: *Kelly Parkes, University of Colorado - Boulder*

Discussant: *Amy Belinda Lewis, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

93.044. Motivation in Online Learning Environments. SIG-

Online Teaching and Learning; Paper Session

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, San Gabriel B; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Lived Experiences of Graduate Students in Online Statistics Courses: Motivation, Anxiety, and Attitudes. *Stephanie Cho, Florida Gulf Coast University; Jingshun Zhang, Florida Gulf Coast University; Xiaoxue Wang, Florida Gulf Coast University*

Examining Self-Regulated Learning Skills among College Students in Asynchronous Online Discussions. *Jiarui Xie, The Ohio State University; Ana-Paula Correia, The Ohio State University*

Measuring Motivation for Online Teaching and Learning in Higher Education. *Julie Brockman Smart, Anderson University; Anna Henshaw Morrison, Clemson University; Luke Bennett, Baylor University; Daphne Wiles, Clemson University*

Teachers' Knowledge Matters: How TPACK Relates to Instructors' Motivation and Technostress. *Yin Hong Cheah, University of Idaho; Shengjie Lin, University of New Mexico*

Using the Motivated Strategies for Learning Questionnaire (MSLQ) To Describe Latent Profiles of Online Learners: Examination across Nine Academic Years. *Li Cao, University of West Georgia; Diana L. Mindrila, University of West Georgia*

Chair: *Dessy S. Stoycheva, University of Northern Iowa*

93.045. Artificial Intelligence, Learning, or Teaching. SIG-

Philosophical Studies in Education; Paper Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 301B; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Beyond the Best Practice Binary: Articulating 'Relational Potential' in Pedagogy. *Samantha Elizabeth Piede, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Does AI have a Place in Education: A Perfectionist Approach to EdTech Ethics. *John Wesley Jones, SUNY Cortland*

From Comprehension to Interpretation: Rethinking the Nature of Literacy. *Maya Alkateb-Chami, Harvard University*

Knowing Ourselves with AI: A Modified Tool-Assisted Approach. *Soomin Nam, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Chair: *Adma Emanuelle Gama-Krummel, University of Rochester*

93.046. Dwelling in the In-Between: Relational and Sensory Turns in Qualitative Inquiry. SIG-Qualitative Research;

Paper Session

InterContinental Los Angeles Downtown, 5th Floor, Boyle Heights; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Unforgetting Autoethnography's Origins: Historical Roots and Futures of Autoethnography in Education Research. *Marcus B. Weaver-Hightower, Virginia Tech*

Hearing Atmospheres: Toward a Relational Acoustemology.

Kimberly A. Powell, Pennsylvania State University

Neurodivergent Unknowing as Educational Research

Methodology. *Meaghan Krazinski, Curry College; Nathan Hughes, Syracuse University*

Inhabiting the In-Between: Reflections on Methodological Displacement. *Chloe Fann, University of Memphis; Chelsea D. Liddell, University of Memphis*

Resisting Linguistic Hegemony in Critical and Participatory Qualitative Methodologies through Reverse Language Shift. *Pengfei Zhao, McGill University; Melissa Hauber-Özer, University of Missouri; Meagan Call-Cummings, Johns Hopkins University; Jesse Van Divier, Johns Hopkins University; Heather Mehrtens, University of Maryland, College Park*

Chair: *Tanushree Sarkar, University of Missouri*

93.047. Creativity, AI, and Learning. SIG-Research on

Giftedness, Creativity and Talent; Paper Session

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Santa Barbara C; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Artificial Intelligence and the Future of Creativity in Higher Education: Faculty Perspectives Across Disciplines.

Fangfang Mo, Purdue University; Yao Yang, Purdue University

Latent Profiles of Personality and Imagination: Examining Sex Differences Across College Disciplines. *Kristen N. Lamb,*

University of Alabama; Lindsay Ellis Lee, Advanced Learning Research & Consulting, LLC

Self-rated Originality as a Mediator that Connects Creative Activities and AI-rated Originality in Divergent Thinking.

Yoojoong Kim, University of Georgia; Denis Dumas, University of Georgia

The Surprising Negative Link Between Creative Extracurricular Activities and Creative Thinking in PISA 2022. *Sofia*

Kagan, University of Georgia; Denis Dumas, University of Georgia; Yoojoong Kim, University of Georgia

Chair: *Tamra Stambaugh, Whitworth University*

Discussant: *Todd Kettler, Baylor University*

93.048. Science Teaching and Learning Across Contexts. SIG-

Science Teaching and Learning; Paper Session

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, San Fernando; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Leveraging Modeling Activities to Enact Responsive Teaching Strategies. *Rida Munir, Utah State University; Hillary Lucille Swanson, Utah State University; Jared Arnell, Utah State University; Ravi Sinha, Utah State University; Idris Solola, Utah State University*

Quantitative Reasoning in Biology Labs: Impacts of Setting and Attitude on Undergraduate Students' Depth of Noticing. *Joelle Prate, Chapman University; Jeremy Hsu, Chapman University*

When Should We Draw? Drawing as a Retrieval Practice in Science Learning. *Feng Shan, East China Normal University; Zhe Wang, East China Normal University; YuMeng Deng, East China Normal University*

Teachers' Use of Generative Artificial Intelligence for Designing Science Lessons to Support Environmental Science Agency. *Won Jung Kim, Santa Clara University*

Tensions and Trade-Offs in Sensemaking Opportunities for Student-Driven Epistemic Agency in Elementary Science. *Christine Lee Bae, Virginia Commonwealth University; Erin K. Hogan, University of Louisville; Kathryn N. Hayes, California State University - East Bay*

Chair: *Miranda M. Allen, Texas Tech University*

93.049. Collaborative Self-Study as Co-construction of Embodied Knowledge in Teacher Education. SIG-Self-Study of Teacher Education Practices; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 9;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Theoretical Frameworks for Exploring Teacher Educator Knowledge and Professional Learning. *Diane Yendol-Hoppey, University of North Florida; Jennifer L. Snow, Boise State University*

Methods and Protocols for Collaborative Self-Study of Enacted Teacher Educator Practice. *Jennifer Jacobs, University of South Florida; Fernando Naiditch, Montclair State University; Frank Pignatosi, New York University; Andrew J. Schiera, University of Colorado - Boulder*

The Power of a Slice: Building Community through Collaborative, Reflective Practice. *Carrie A. Nepstad, City Colleges of Chicago; Frances OC Rust, University of Pennsylvania*

Teacher Education Research IS Teacher Education Practice. *Connor Warner, University of Utah; Dirck Roosevelt, Independent Scholar*

Chair: *Stefnee E. Pinnegar, Brigham Young University*

Discussant: *Brandon M. Butler, Old Dominion University*

93.050. When We Unforget Trauma, Developmental Accountability Becomes Possible. SIG-Stress, Coping, and Resilience; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 306B;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Emerging Strategies for Engaging Vulnerable Populations in Research with the Life Graph with Cards Method. *Ana Beard, University of Montana - Missoula; Krista L. Goldstine-Cole, University of Montana; Siwen Zhang Minero, University of Montana*

Unforgetting the Forgotten: A Life course Perspective on Chronic Houselessness in Rural America. *Siwen Zhang Minero, University of Montana; Ana Beard, University of Montana - Missoula*

“School-to-Prison Pipeline” as Forgetting Dynamic, Interrelated Risk: What Currently Incarcerated Men Need Us to Remember. *Jeffery Chaichana Peterson, University of Montana; Krista L. Goldstine-Cole, University of Montana*

Collective Trauma and the Imperative of Unforgetting: Toward a Trauma-Informed Educator Workforce. *Natalie Turner-Depue, Washington State University*

Chair: *Krista L. Goldstine-Cole, University of Montana*

Discussant: *Maung Ting Nyeu, University of California - Santa Barbara*

93.051. Students Placed At Promise for Academic Success! Dr. A. Wade Boykin's Talent Development Legacy. SIG-Talent Development of Students Placed at Risk; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum I;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Equity Aspiration: Why Historically Excluded STEM Students Turn to Entrepreneurship. *Binh Chi Bui, The University of Texas at El Paso; Shelly Engelman, Johns Hopkins University; Ebony O. McGee, Johns Hopkins University*

Toward the Development of a Black Teacher Census: Reclaiming Voice, Visibility, and Validity. *Christopher D. Hill, Black Teacher Collaborative; Ashley Griffin Gilchrist, Bowie State University; Shelly Engelman, Johns Hopkins University*

Verve in College? Examining the Developmental and Population Ranges of Culturally Relevant Pedagogy. *Eric A. Hurley, Pomona College*

Chair: *R. Davis Dixon, Howard University*

Discussant: *Sean T. Coleman, Bowie State University*

93.052. Unforgetting Multiple Histories and Imagining Multiple Futures of Asian(American) Im/migrant Literacies. SIG-Writing and Literacies; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Plaza I;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Countering Erasure: Vietnamese American Bilingual Children Learning Wars, Armed Conflicts, and Genocide Through Multilingual Literacies. *Alisha Nguyen, Lesley University*
Chinese American Children Interrogating Race Through Asian-Crit-Informed Racial Literacy in a Community-Based

Book Club. *Wenyu Guo, University of South Florida;*
Yuechen Sun, University of South Carolina

Tracing Asian American Youths' Transnational Civic
Literacies through Youth Participatory Action Research.
Ankhi Guha Thakurta, Boston College

Unforgetting Care as Family History: The Intergenerational and
Transnational Relational Literacies of a Chinese
Transnational Family. *Tairan Qiu, Stanford University*

Photo Essay as Autoethnographic Multimodal Ensembles:
Learning from the Compositional Practices of Two South
Asian American University Students. *Mohit P. Mehta, Texas
State University*

Chairs: *Tairan Qiu, Stanford University; Wenyu Guo, University of
South Florida*

Discussant: *Guofang Li, University of British Columbia*

Division and SIG Roundtables

93.053. AERA Roundtable Session Sunday 11:45 am; Roundtable Session

93.053-1. Moving Beyond Textbook Authority (Table 1). Division B - Curriculum Studies; Roundtable Session Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

From Authority to Resource to Carrier: Textbook Positioning in
Chinese Policy Discourse. *yulin ma, East China Normal
University; Hao Lei, East China Normal University*

From Chinese Nationalism to Taiwanism: Political Power,
Identity, and Unforgetting Cultural Histories in Taiwan's
Elementary Curriculum. *Ming-Chu Hsu, Indiana University
Bloomington*

Ideological Entanglements in Literacy Instruction:

Translanguaging, White Monolingualism, and the Influence
of the Science of Reading Abstract. *Laurie Elisabet Hahn
Ganser, University of Minnesota*

Chair: *Jonggeun Park, Teachers College, Columbia University*

93.053-2. Critical Cartographies: Centering Teacher Knowledge in Place, Identity, and Curriculum Justice (Table 2). Division B - Curriculum Studies; Roundtable Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Curriculum at the Crossroads: Reimagining Rural Curriculum
Through Community Memory and Educational Justice.
Alicia Francisca Noreiga, Acadia University

Teachers' Knowledge Work and Curriculum Thinking: Insights
from a Working Ethnic Studies Curriculum Collective. *Kelly
León, University of Wisconsin - Green Bay*

Theorizing Aztlán: A critical exploration model of culture and

place with Chicana pre-service teachers. *Raul Garza,
University of Texas - Rio Grande Valley; James C. Jupp,
University of Texas - Rio Grande Valley*

Why Do Rural Teachers in China Hardly Implement the
Curriculum Reform? A Social Ecosystem Perspective. *Yu-
Wen Wang, Henan Normal University*

Chair: *Aya M. Isaac, University at Albany - SUNY*

93.053-3. Healing and Empowerment in Counseling (Table 3). Division E - Counseling and Human Development; Roundtable Session Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Breathing Room: Reclaiming Somatic Knowledge in Counselor
Education for Liberation and Healing. *Zoya A McCants, St.
John's University*

Healing Amid War: Thematic Analysis of Counseling
Outcomes for Children Treated at Psychological
Rehabilitation Camps. *Aaron Albright, Old Dominion
University; Lauren Robins, Old Dominion University; Shana
L. Pribesh, Old Dominion University; Busra Vurkun, Old
Dominion University; Tammi Dice, Old Dominion
University; Emily C. Goodman-Scott, Old Dominion
University*

Latent Profile Analysis of Youth Social-Emotional Adjustment,
Prosocial Behavior, and Academic Competence. *Gen Li,
University of South Florida; Jie Luo, University of
Connecticut*

Voices Unhoused: Pathways to Empowerment for Students in
Temporary Housing. *Qiana Spellman, St. John's University;
Shannah M. Henderson Amare, New York City Department
of Education; Kelly Kent, Antioch University - Los Angeles*

Chair: *Dashana Lane, Bethune Cookman University*

93.053-4. Towards Global Perspectives on Education (Table 4). Division F - Historical Inquiry in Education; Roundtable Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Blame and Buttress: Higher Education and the Defense of
Democracy. *Allison Palmadessa, Greensboro College;
Ethan W. Ris, University of Nevada - Reno*

Chinese Educational Mobility to the United States: A Historical
Perspective. *Jing Yu, University of Wisconsin - Madison*
Cycles of Dissent: Unforgetting Student Protest and
Educational Governance in California, 1945–2024. *Yi Wu,
Pennsylvania State University*

Disciplinary Vectors of Secular Reform: A Biographical
Network Analysis of German-Jewish Scholars in Turkish
Higher Education. *Seyma Aksoy, Yıldız Technical University
Türkiye*

Junior No More? Revisiting Historical Constraints on the

Community College. *Ethan W. Ris, University of Nevada - Reno*

Chair: *Seyma Aksoy, Yıldız Technical University Türkiye*

93.053-5. Educational Uncertainty, Liminal Space and Black Futures (Table 5). Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

A Multicase Study of African Entrepreneurs' Perceptions Ten Years After a US Fellowship Exchange Program. *Lisa K. Taylor, University of Nevada, Reno; Jessica Gallo, University of Nevada - Reno; Joyce Nabisaalu, University of North Carolina - Greensboro*

Living Frozen : The Temporal Struggles of Gaokao Repeaters in China. *Yang Chen, Zhejiang University; Chang Liu, Zhejiang University*

Re-imagining Black Educational Futures for Black youth: A University Multi-School Partnership in Vancouver, Canada. *Annette M. Henry, University of British Columbia*

Selective Suspension: Navigating Educational Uncertainty among Second-Time Postgraduate Candidates in China. *可 可 王, East China Normal University*

93.053-6. Global Contexts, Educational Access and Learning (Table 6). Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Sustaining Noticing as Potential: US Teacher Candidates in Aotearoa New Zealand Schools. *Lori Czop Assaf, Texas State University; Jessica Cira Rubin, University of Waikato*

Marketing Merit: Neoliberal Politics of Asian American Representation in a Charter School. *Insil Jeon, University of Minnesota*

Beyond Rescue: Child Trafficking, Educational Access and Reintegration in Eastern Sierra Leone. *Liu Liu, University of Georgia; Anna Cody, University of Georgia; David Okech, University of Georgia; Hui Yi, University of Georgia; Anne Waswa, University of Georgia; Pedro Goulart, University of Georgia*

93.053-7. Agency and Ideologies (Table 7). Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Empowerment in Complexity: A child's Agency and A Mother's Pluralistic Ideologies Amidst Hegemonic Ideologies. *Eunjin Cho, University of Massachusetts - Amherst*

Unforgetting Through Digital Storytelling: Literacy, Identity, and Voice for Afghan Refugee Women. *Melissa Wicker, Tarleton State University; Jiening Ruan, University of Oklahoma; Jacey Ford, University of Oklahoma*

The Weight of the Wake: Mapping the Emotional Geographies of Black Study. *Amber Neal-Stanley, Purdue University; Kayla Fisher, Purdue University; Ralph J. McCoy, Purdue University; Gerald Mwansa, Purdue University; Christabel Kanayo Anumenechi, Purdue University; Julius Freeman, Purdue University*

93.053-8. Translanguaging (Table 8). Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Translanguaging and The 1619 Project: How a Salvadoran-American 3rd grader made sense of African enslavement. *Audrey Lensmire, Augsburg University*

Translanguaging, Systemic Functional Linguistics, and Artificial Intelligence in K-12 Science Classrooms: A Multiple Case Study. *Kaycie D Barron, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Shamyia Karumbaiah, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Mariana Castro, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Cynthia T. Baeza, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Translanguaging Pedagogy in Two-way Dual Language Bilingual Education: A Qualitative meta-analysis. *Jung Won Hyun, Ewha Womans University*

Applying a Translanguaging Perspective to Collaborative Problem-Solving. *Collin Pitts, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Gengqi Xiao, University of Wisconsin-Madison; Shamyia Karumbaiah, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Kaycie D Barron, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Mariana Castro, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Pragati Maheshwary, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Chair: *Jaclyn B. Bovee, Oregon State University*

93.053-9. Knowing and Learning in Context (Table 9). Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Combatting AI Hype with Participatory Audits: Critical AI Literacy in K-12 Contexts. *Thema Monroe-White, George Mason University; Evan Shieh, Young Data Scientists League*

Fragmented Perspectives, Flattened Faces: Narrative Inquiry and Identity Representation in Immigrant Lives. *Hua Hua, University of Calgary*

Hope as Survival and Resistance: Social-Emotional Strategies of Girls Navigating Adversity in a Kenyan Slum. *Hyunju Lee, University of Oklahoma; Zainabu M. Momanyi, University of Oklahoma*

“The Hierarchy of Knowledge”: Deciphering Man Within Computer Science Disciplinary Values. *Natalie Araujo Melo, Northwestern University*

Chair: *Hua Luo, Florida State University*

93.053-10. Bourdieu and Inequalities (Table 10). SIG-Bourdieu in Educational Research; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Disrupting Systemic and Systematic Educational Inequalities Through Legitimizing Racialized Non-Dominant Students' Power for Transformation. *Sophina Choudry, University of Manchester*

Low-Socioeconomic Status Students and Decision-Making behind Sorority Membership. *Sarah Ann Harris, Baylor University; Saralyn McKinnon-Crowley, Baylor University; Hunter Kulesza, Baylor University; Tiffani Hoot, Baylor University*

Service in the Shadows: Faculty of Color, Community Engagement, and the Politics of Academic Recognition. *Toyosi Stephen Adedara, Baylor University*

93.054. AERA Roundtable Session Sunday 11:45 am - Gold 1;
Roundtable Session

93.054-1. Community College Experiences and Perspectives (Table 1). Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Leveraging Asset-Based Peer Tutoring for Equity in Emerging Hispanic Serving Community Colleges. *Brooklyn Cole Herrera, University of North Georgia; Michael Lanford, University of North Georgia*

Service Learning as a Pathway to Enhanced Belonging: A Multi-Institutional Study of Community College Students. *Bingyao Hu, Johns Hopkins University*

Discussant: *Halkano Michael Hargura, Texas Tech University*

93.054-2. Roundtable 6 (Table 2). Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Learning from leavers: Early academic predictors of engineering attrition via machine learning. *Lydia Ross, Arizona State University; Amanda J. Davis Simpfenderfer, College of William & Mary; Travis Terpkosh, Arizona State University; Junzhao Wang, Arizona State University*

How Perceived Goal Attainment Shapes Student Satisfaction: The Chain Mediating Roles of Competence Acquisition,

Learning, and Infrastructure. *Yan Chunshun, East China Normal University; Mengting Qian, East China Normal University; Tianyi Sun, East China Normal University; Shiqi Teng, Jishou University*

Comparison of Logistic Regression and Generalized Estimating Equations Models for predicting Student Persistence. *Meng-Jia Wu, Loyola University Chicago*

93.054-3. Curricular and Instructional Models for the Future (Table 3). Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Expressions of Faculty Activism in the Natural Sciences: The Development of a Typology. *Katalin Szelenyi, University of Massachusetts - Boston; Willord Simmons, Harvard University*

Faculty Engagement in Curriculum Internationalization: A Comparative Review of Chinese and Japanese Higher Education. *Rong Wang, Xi'an Jiaotong-Liverpool University; Mina Mizumatsu, Toyo University*

The Power of Partnership: Co-Teaching Opportunities and Challenges in Developmental Education. *Susana H. Hernandez, Northern Arizona University; Lyle McKinney, University of North Florida; Andrea Backscheider Burrridge, Houston Community College; Amy Tan, Connecticut State Community College*

Chair: *Ashley N. Gaskew, Baruch College - CUNY*

93.054-4. Division J Section 6: Roundtable 5 (Table 4). Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Navigating Academic Fields: PhD Graduate Capital and Academic Employment in China. *Xiaoli Jing, Beijing Normal University; Sitong Wang, McGill University*

Reimagining Graduate Education: The Doctor of Arts Degree and the Formation of the Scholarly Teaching Identity. *Kirsten Tekavec, Pennsylvania State University*

Reviving the Revolution: Teen Summit 2.0 and the Communiversity Model for Youth Civic Engagement Through Public Media. *Malaika McKee, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Unmaking the Ableist University: Autistic College Students and the Call to Reimagine Higher Education. *Yasmine Pandjaitan, University of California - Santa Cruz*

93.054-5. Retooling on the Job: Technology, AI and Digital Tools for Teacher Educators (Table 5). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

- Enhancing Teacher Educators' Digital Training Competence Through Transformative Learning: A Quasi-Experimental Study. *Rui Jiang, Beijing Normal University; Yushun Li, Beijing Normal University*
- Navigating AI in Teacher Education: Faculty's Critical Perspectives on Preparing Pre-Service Teachers. *Rosa Angela Calosso, Graduate Center - CUNY; Yesim Nur Akar Hozman, Michigan State University; Aman Yadav, Michigan State University*
- Teaching What We Don't Yet Know: A Collaborative Self-Study of Teacher Educators Navigating Generative AI. *Katie Trautman, University of Texas at Austin; Emily McDonald, University of Texas at Austin; Laura Iris Sanchez, University of Texas at Austin; Amanda Smith, University of Texas at Austin*

Chair: *Rick J. Voithofer, The Ohio State University*

93.054-6. Innovations in Teacher Learning: Cognitive Apprenticeship, Feedback, and Technology Integration (Table 6). Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

- Exploring and Comparing the Self-efficacy of Veteran Grade 4 Science Teachers in the use of Interactive Simulations for instruction. *Ehimwenma Orobator, University of Kentucky; Lin Xiang, University of Kentucky*
- Exploring Ethical and Innovative Teaching Practices with TPACK and FATE in Higher Education. *Zixi Li, Indiana University; Chaoran Wang, Colby College; Meina Zhu, Wayne State University*
- Feedback Landscape in Preservice Teacher Education: A Systematic Literature Review of Sources, Methods, and Technologies. *Michael Otieno Okumu, Texas Tech University; Catherine A. Lammert, Texas Tech University; Ceren Gokmen, Texas Tech University; Felix Mule, Texas Tech University*
- From Invisible Intuition to Observable Action: Rethinking Pedagogical Tact through Simulation-Triggered Judgment. *Mengyan Wei, East China Normal University; Yuanyuan Li, Shanghai Normal University*
- Prompt-Engineered Cognitive Apprenticeship for In-Service K-9 Teacher Learning. *Alberto Cureg Cruz, California State University, Bakersfield; Anjana Yatawara, California State University, Bakersfield; Maruti Mishra, California State University, Bakersfield; Jianjun Wang, California State University - Bakersfield*

Chair: *Ilene Ivins, Alder Graduate School of Education*

93.055. AERA Roundtable Session Sunday 11:45 am - Gold 2;
Roundtable Session

93.055-1. Immigrant Students and Intersectional Inequality (Table 1). Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

- Contextual Factors and School Adjustment of Multicultural Elementary Students: A Longitudinal Study in South Korea. *Yeseul Doo, University of Chicago*
- Racialized and Administrative Burdens in IDEA: Examining the Experiences of Im/migrant and Refugee Families. *Adai A. Tefera, University of Arizona; Melissa J. Cuba, University of Maine*
- Strategic Inclusion: Interest Convergence in Higher Education Policy for Immigrant Students. *Deyaneira Daniza Chic, University of California - Berkeley*
- Towards a Critical College Choice Model for Undocumented Students. *Diego Castro Gomez, University of California - Los Angeles*

Chair: *Sandra Barrueco, The Catholic University of America*

93.055-2. Digging Deeper: Transforming Practice Through Lesson Study: Core Insights, Empathy, and Critical Perspectives (Table 2). SIG-Lesson Study; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

- Empathy-Driven Lesson Study: The Case of the Community Garden Design-based Lesson. *Gloriana Gonzalez, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Sourabh Garg, University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign; Jane Pak, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*
- Lesson Study: Unpacking a Lesson on Cultural Icebergs Through a Critical Friend Lens. *Lisa Rose Johnson, Old Dominion University*
- Teacher and Leader Insights on the Core Components of Lesson Study. *Meghan Smith Durkin, Stanford University; Marley Angelita Murrell, Stanford University; Hilda Borko, Stanford University*

Chair: *Karie C. Brown, Georgia State University*

93.055-3. Belonging and Identity Across Borders (Table 3). SIG-Multicultural/Multiethnic Education: Theory, Research and Practice; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

- Emotional Belonging in Transnational English Language Teaching: A Black American Woman Teacher's Experiences in Korea. *Jiheia Maddamsetti, Old Dominion University*
- Navigating Racial and Ethnic Barriers: Experiences of an International Graduate Student TA-ing and Supervising Pre-Service Teachers in a Midwestern U.S. University. *Charity*

Ulunma Okpara, UW Madison

The Futures We Bring: Cultural Worldviews and the Reimagining of Academic Belonging. *Ya-Li Wu, Fo Guang University; Yanty Wirza, Indonesia University of Education; David Bwire, The College of New Jersey*

Chair: *Jennifer M. Bondy, Arizona State University*

93.055-4. From Preparation to Leadership: Supporting Rural Teachers Through Identity, Networks, and Community (Table 4). SIG-Rural Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Building Rural K-12 Leadership Pipeline: Outcomes of a Teacher Leadership Academy. *Hamada Elfarargy, South Dakota State University; Anne Karabon, South Dakota State University; Patrick D. Hales, South Dakota State University*

Known Face, New Role: A Qualitative Case Study of a Homegrown Rural Teacher. *Caiden Webb, University of Missouri; Laura Zangori, University of Missouri; Laura Cole, Colorado State University*

Remedy & Renewal in Northern California's Rural Teacher Residencies. *Imelda Nava-Landeros, University of California - Los Angeles; Sheila Rocker Heppel, State Residency Technical Assistance Center*

Teacher Preparation Influences on New Teachers' Decisions to Teach Rural: Insights from a Multi-Institutional Study. *Devon G. Brenner, Mississippi State University; Diana Cumings Outlaw, Mississippi State University; Dana P. Franz, Mississippi State University*

What Keeps Rural STEM Teachers Teaching? A Multiple Regression Analysis. *Woongbin Park, Purdue University; Jung Han, Purdue University; Yu-Chieh Wu, University of Hawai'i at Mānoa; Todd R. Kelley, Purdue University*

Chair: *Meghan Moore-Hubbard, Kennesaw State University*

93.055-5. Educational Psychology and Literacy Development: Examining the role of Affective and Psychological Factors in Language Learning (Table 5). SIG-Second Language Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Beyond Fixed or Growth - Uncovering Diverse Mindset Profiles in Language Learners. *Pengpeng Cai, Trinity College Dublin; Xuhong Li, City University of Hong Kong; Xin Guan, Hong Kong Baptist University*

Developing Dual-Language Materials for Science Classrooms: Psychology-Informed Approaches. *Onur Ramazan, University of Hong Kong; Yuliya Ardasheva, Washington State University - Tri Cities; Lindsay K. Lightner, Washington State University; Shenghai Dai, Washington State University; Anne Marie Guerrettaz, Washington State University; Gamze Karaer, Washington State University;*

Danica Garcia, Washington State University - Tri-Cities; Gladys C. Suarez, Washington State University; Yun-Ju Hsiao, Washington State University - Tri-Cities

Personality-Driven Acceptance of ChatGPT in Language Learning: An Extended TAM Approach. *Mi Tang, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Yiran Du, University of Cambridge*

The Emotional Equation: A Mixed Methods Approach into Affective Factors Shaping AI-Assisted ESL Writing Through a Positive Psychology Lens. *Xiangning Li, University of Cambridge; YUNAN ZHANG, University of Hong Kong; Belle Li, Purdue University*

Chair: *Andrea Louise Ochoa, Brown University*

93.055-6. EFL in Global Contexts: Shared Reading, Visual Narratives, and Innovative Approaches to Literacy (Table 6). SIG-Second Language Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

The Impact of Visual Literacy Instruction on EFL Students' Comprehension of Multimodal Texts. *Daibao Guo, Boise State University; Lin Gou, Boise State University; Eun Hye Son, Boise State University; Qizhen Deng, Boise State University; Michelle A. Satterfield, Boise State University*

Visual Narratives to Stimulate English Reading in Colombian Adults: A Pedagogical Intervention Based on the Four-phase Model of Interest. *Aura Caterine Quilismal Prieto, Universidad Nacional de Colombia; Andy Parra Martinez, Mississippi State University*

Group Size Effects on English Production in Young Japanese Learners. *Hee Jin Bang, Age of Learning; Alison Mackey, Georgetown University; Akiko Fujii, International Christian University*

93.055-7. Systems, Policies, and Effective Inclusive Education (Table 7). SIG-Special and Inclusive Education Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Understanding Personalization and Individualization from Education Policy Perspectives: Towards an Integrated School-Wide Implementation System. *Ling Zhang, University of Wyoming*

A Tale of Two States: Educational Service Agencies, Access, and Outcomes for Students With Disabilities. *Julia M. White, Syracuse University; Qiu Wang, Syracuse University; Christine Elaine Ashby, Syracuse University; Rebekah Wallis, Syracuse University; Yehyang Lee, Syracuse University*

More than Rhetoric: A Case Study of Inclusive Education Policy and Practice. *Megan Murray, University of*

Massachusetts - Boston

Chair: *Heather M. Dulas, University of Houston*

93.055-8. Technology and Innovation in Special and Education

(Table 8). SIG-Special and Inclusive Education Research;

Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Preliminary Teaching Manual for Classroom IEP Support: An AI-assisted, Collaborative Delphi Inquiry. *Laurie Faith, University of Toronto - OISE; Qiyuan Zheng, University of Toronto - OISE; Lisa VanderKuip, University of Toronto - OISE; Nadine Masengi, Edvance; Samantha Price, Edvance; Rebecca Dam, Edvance*

Optimizing Embedded Assessment in NumberShire Gaming Intervention: Response Time and Accuracy Trade-offs. *Sam Choo, University of Minnesota; Jechun An, University of Minnesota; Nancy J. Nelson, Boston University; Derek Kosty, Oregon Research Institute*

Cognitive Offloading in the Age of Generative AI: What Does It Mean for Students with Learning Disabilities? *Yerin Seung, University of Kansas; James D. Basham, University of Kansas*

Chair: *Amanda Banks, East Tennessee State University*

93.056. AERA Roundtable Session Sunday 11:45 am - Gold 3;

Roundtable Session

93.056-1. Critical Examination of AI's Role in Education

(Table 1). SIG-Technology as an Agent of Change in Teaching and Learning; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Beyond AI Literacy: Technoskepticism and Positioning Theory in Teacher Education About AI. *Jacob Pleasants, University of Oklahoma; Julianna E. Lopez Kershen, University of Oklahoma*

Knowledge Risks in the Age of Generative AI: Epistemological Shifts and Educational Responses. *Tianjian WANG, Guangzhou University*

Instruction by Proxy? Pedagogical Design, Faculty Agency, and the Uneven Work of Teaching with AI. *Jorge Martinez Cortes, Universidad Veracruzana; Emmy Min, University of Southern California; Jenifer Crawford, University of Southern California; Isai Ali Guevara Bazan, Universidad Veracruzana; Corinne Hyde, University of Southern California; Ekaterina Moore, University of Southern California; Robert A. Filback, University of Southern California*

Toward a Critical, Technology-Integrated Curriculum. *Shuning Liu, Ball State University; Charles P. Tuite, Ball State University*

Unforgetting Digital Exclusions: A Critical Framework for Inclusive EdTech Futures. *Elham Maleki, University of Nevada - Reno*

Chair: *Joshua Littenberg-Tobias, GBH*

93.056-2. Teachers' Perspectives, Readiness and Experiences in the Post-COVID AI Era (Table 2). SIG-Technology as an Agent of Change in Teaching and Learning; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;

11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Exploring AI Readiness Through Teachers' Self-Efficacy and Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK). *Carlos Manrique Perez, Texas A&M University; Mahjabin Chowdhury, Texas A&M University*

Exploring Teacher Perspectives on Contemporary Complexities in K-12 ICT Integration. *Jeffrey P. Carpenter, Elon University; Bianca S. Bиаdeni, Escola Superior de Propaganda e Marketing*

Undergraduate Perceptions of AI Tools in Higher Education: A Mixed-Methods Exploration. *Burhan Ozfidan, Florida Gulf Coast University; Santiago Luaces, Florida Gulf Coast University; Christa Reyes, Florida Gulf Coast University; Nika Verna, Florida Gulf Coast University*

Medical Students' Adoption and Perceptions of ChatGPT for EFL Academic Writing in Wartime Ukraine. *Haiyan Li, Purdue University; Lixia Cheng, Purdue University; Violeta Kalnytska, Purdue University*

Chair: *Carlos Manrique Perez, Texas A&M University*

93.056-3. Reimagining Teaching: Disability Identity, Culture, and Anti-Ableism in K-12 Education (Table 3). SIG-

Disability Studies in Education; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Culturally Responsive Teaching Practices to Support Students with Visual Impairments in Illinois: Are We Ready? *Eric R. Junco, Northern Illinois University*

Interrogating Intersectionality in Advocating for Multilingual Learners: Teacher Narratives within Multi-Tiered Systems of Support. *Meredith McConnochie, University of Saint Joseph; Haerin Park, University of Saint Joseph*

"I recognize his traits so much in myself": Anti-ableist Teaching Practices Informed by Disabled Educators' Expertise. *Amy Leigh Tondreau, University of Maryland - Baltimore County; Laurie M. Rabinowitz, Skidmore College; Katryna Andrusik, University of Maryland*

Chair: *Kelly Ann Peña, Rutgers University*

93.056-4. (Re)Imagining Early Literacy, Care, and Criticality (Table 4). SIG-Language and Social Processes; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Becoming a Writer in PreK: Constructing Writing Practices and Identities in Collaborative “Live Writing” Events. *Deborah Rowe, Vanderbilt University; Erica Lee Payne, Vanderbilt University*

“I Draw Mommy Right Here...Wearing Mask”: Care, Criticality, and Crip Linguistics through Early Childhood Literacy. *Maggie Beneke, University of Washington; Emily Machado, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Jordan Taitingfong, University of Washington*

Writing Outside the Lines: Reimagining Writing Instruction Through Multilingual Students’ Speech Bubbles. *Megumi Takada, Stanford University*

Anchoring Ethnographic Research in the Logic of Children. *Daniel Edelen, Georgia State University; Audra Skukauskaite, University of Central Florida*

Chair: *Deborah Rowe, Vanderbilt University*

93.056-5. Translanguaging as Praxis: Negotiating Multilingualism, Power, and Pedagogy (Table 5). SIG-Language and Social Processes; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

English Language Learners Learn Life Cycles Through Translanguaging and Dialogic Discourse. *Christelle Fayad, Texas Christian University; Hayat Hokayem, Texas Christian University; Sara Salloum, Ohio University*

Translanguaging in Practice: Examining Teacher–Student Interaction in a SIFE Literacy Classroom. *Abbey E Gonzales, Vanderbilt University*

“That’s Not How We Speak”: Korean-American Youth Reposition Hybrid Speech as Evidence of Multilingual Fluency. *Hala Sun, Michigan State University; Hye-In Yang, Michigan State University*

Chair: *Munira Kairat, University of California - Santa Barbara*

93.056-6. What Does will Shape The Future: Navigating Complex Educational Issues Across Nations (Table 6). SIG-International Studies; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Should Your Title Pose a Question? Predicting Citations for Articles in International Higher Education Journals. *Nicholas A. Bowman, University of Iowa; Sze Ling Hung, University of Iowa; Teniell L. Trolan, University at Albany - SUNY*

Towards a Pluralistic and Cross-Cultural Understanding of Critical Thinking: Moving Beyond Anglo-Centric Models in Global Higher Education. *Luman Zhou, University of Manchester*

Multilevel Determinants of School Belonging: The Moderating Role of National Safety Climate. *Shreya Malla, University of Kansas; Jose Fabian Elizondo-Gonzalez, University of Kansas; Solange Barros, University of Kansas*
Chair: *Sabahet S. Bruncaj, United Arab Emirates University*

93.056-7. Leadership and engagement: Building equitable partnership (Table 7). SIG-Family, School, Community Partnerships; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Daily Routines and Parental Time Investment: New Directions for Futuring Equitable Family-School-Community Partnerships. *Soojin Oh Park, University of Washington; Carla Asiedu-Ofei, University of Washington*

Parental engagement in charter school board governance/. *Charisse A. Gulosino, University of Memphis; Elif Sisli Ciamarra, Stonehill College*

Reflecting on Past and Future: Proposing a Lakatosian Research Programme for Towards Advancing Family-School Partnerships. *Thomas J Capretta, The Ohio State University*

Chair: *Thomas J Capretta, The Ohio State University*

93.056-8. Learning from International Context: Promoting Home-School Engagement (Table 8). SIG-Family, School, Community Partnerships; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Between Structure and Agency: A Qualitative Study of Institutionalization and Parental Involvement in Chinese Primary Schools. *Yuting Wang, Beijing Normal University; Xiaohang Luo, University of Pennsylvania*

Empowering Parents to Protect Children Against Online Risks Through Digital Parenting: An Umbrella Review. *Mengyi Liang, University of Hong Kong; Cheng Yong Tan, University of Hong Kong; Naiqi Xu, The University of Hong Kong*

From family toward school and society: A representative practice of intergenerational learning sustainably created in China. *Hao Cheng, Central China Normal University; Qiqi Zhang, Central China Normal University; Zhiping Mai, Central China Normal University; Hongfeng Yang, Wuhan Institute of Technology*

Holding Space for Change: Educational Systems Responding to Transnational Mobility. *Borui Zheng, Trinity College Dublin*

Chair: *Michael Ota, Kennesaw State University*

93.056-9. Reclaiming Knowledge, Reimagining Futures: Latiné Youth, Families, and Cultural Pedagogies of Resistance (Table 9). SIG-Latina/o/x Research Issues; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

- Con Confianza: Postsecondary Pathways for Suburban Latinx Youth. *Melissa Ortiz, New York University*
- Cultivating Educational Pathways: Latina/Chicana Mother-Daughter Pedagogies of Hope, Resistance, and Love. *Tracey Terece Flores, University of Texas at Austin*
- Cultural Reproduction of Ancestral Knowledge in Latiné Young Adult Literature: Examining Speculative Worlds to Illuminate Future Possibilities. *Vanessa E. Vega, University of Central Florida*
- Grit, Resilience, and Settler Colonial Logics: A Critical Systematic Review of SEL Literature. *Chelsea Stinson, Binghamton University - SUNY; Jose Ortiz, SUNY Cortland*
- Chair: *Tracey Terece Flores, University of Texas at Austin*

93.057. AERA Roundtable Session Sunday 11:45 am - Gold 4;
Roundtable Session

93.057-1. Reimagining Tutoring and Personalized Learning for Student Success (Table 1). Division H - Research, Evaluation and Assessment in Schools; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

- Evaluating the Effectiveness of a Literacy Tutoring Program Using Propensity Score Matching. *Qiao Liu, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Carl Westine, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Richard G. Lambert, University of North Carolina - Charlotte*
- Teachers can do it with support: Fidelity across a decade of Pathways-to-Success. *Daphna Oyserman, University of Southern California; Alysia Burbidge, University of Southern California; Yahan Huang, University of Southern California; Nicholas A. Sorensen, American Institutes for Research*
- The Impact of Tutoring and Its Modality on High School Students' Postsecondary Enrollment. *Caleb Pollard, Appalachian State University; Jui-Teng Li, Appalachian State University; Corinne Smith, Appalachian State University; Shawn Bergman, Appalachian State University; James Beeler, Appalachian State University; Catherine Parks, Appalachian State University; Hayden Laws, Appalachian State University; Kathryn Watson, Appalachian State University; Shawn McNulty, Appalachian State University*
- The Mindful Classroom: A Study of 'Happy Teachers Change the World' in Special Education. *Matthew Ristau, Notre Dame of Maryland University; Angela L. Snyder, Notre Dame of Maryland University; Mark J. Fenster, Notre Dame of Maryland University; Kristine E. Larson, Notre Dame University of Maryland*

93.057-2. Relational Pedagogy and Belonging: Navigating the Social Dimensions of Student Motivation and Learning (Table 2). Division C - Learning and Instruction
Cosponsored with SIG-Motivation in Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

- Teacher-Student Relations in Practice: Student Perceptions of Positive Teaching. *Orly Shapira, Tel Aviv University; Fadia Naser Abu-Alhija, Tel Aviv University; Benzi Slakmon, Tel Aviv University*
- The Effectiveness of Learning Assistants Matters: Examining Their Role On Sense of Belonging and Self-efficacy. *Kaicheng Zhang, Michigan State University; Cynthia J. Brame, Vanderbilt University; Heather J. Johnson, Vanderbilt University; Sabriya Rosemond, Vanderbilt University; Thomas P. Clements, Vanderbilt University; Cristina D. Zepeda, Vanderbilt University*
- School Climate, Social-emotional Learning, and Learning Achievement: Results from 29 countries/regions of PISA 2022. *Norman B. Mendoza, The Education University of Hong Kong; Jiaying Chen, The Education University of Hong Kong; Yuhan Xiong, Education University of Hong Kong; Le-xuan Zhang, Education University of Hong Kong; Zi Yan, The Education University of Hong Kong*
- How Perceived Teacher-Student Relationship Quality is Associated with Belonging and Emotional Engagement. *Tim Urdan, Santa Clara University; Sofia Eleftheria N. Gonida, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki*
- Students' Views on Social-Contextual Features of Inquiry Supporting Motivation in Middle Grades Science. *Karlyn R. Adams-Wiggins, Portland State University; Toni Kempler Rogat, Purdue University; Jiaying Wang, Purdue University*
- Chair: *Lauren Cabrera, University of Michigan - Dearborn*

93.057-3. Advanced SEM Approaches for Modeling Interaction, Heterogeneity, and Variability (Table 3).
SIG-Structural Equation Modeling and Multilevel Modeling Methods; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

- A Factored Regression Approach to Modeling Interactions Between Latent and Multicategorical Variables. *Remus Rose Mitchell, University of California - Los Angeles; Craig K. Enders, University of California - Los Angeles*
- Detecting differential effects through a moderation model. *Min Liu, Baylor University; Grant B. Morgan, Baylor University; Gregory R. Hancock, University of Maryland; Chih-Pu Dai, Texas A&M University*
- Individual Variability as a Moderator of Structural Equation Model Parameters. *Joshua Shulkin, University of Maryland; Gregory R. Hancock, University of Maryland*

Comparing Structural After Measurement Approaches for Structural Equation Models with Latent Interactions and Missing Data. *Kyle T. Cox, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Benjamin Kelcey, University of Cincinnati; Fangxing Bai, Montana State University*

93.057-4. Contextualizing Educational Data (Table 4). SIG-Survey Research in Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Assessing Methodological Transparency in TIMSS, PIRLS, and PISA Studies: Reporting Practices from 2014–2023. *Yitong Yue, University of Virginia; Rujun Xu, University of Virginia; Bethany A. Bell, University of Virginia*

DIF Analysis of the Sense of School Belonging Scale by Performance and Survey Language. *Henrietta Kadi Tetley-Tawiah, University of Arkansas at Fayetteville; Ronna C. Turner, University of Arkansas*

How Curriculum Context Activates (or Suppresses) Pedagogical Sensitivity: Evidence from a Teacher Survey Experiment. *Chenchen Lu, Purdue University; Rudan Wang, Purdue University*

Linking Student Wellbeing, Attendance, Behavior, and Assessment Data through Structural Equation Modeling. *Davie Store, Kent ISD; Gavin Vance, Kent School District; Stephen Petros, Grand Rapids Public Schools; Peter A. Walblay, Grand Rapids Public Schools; Jennifer Rotach, Kent ISD; Daeja Marzette, Kent Intermediate School District*

93.057-5. Constructing and Contesting Equity in Education Policy (Table 5). Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

What is STEM?: Reframing Policy, Power, and Educational Pathways. *Doug Havard, Chapman University*

Restricting Dialogues on Race and Gender, Reinforcing Dominant Narratives: A Critical Analysis of Tennessee's HB580/SB623. *Julianne Park, New York University*

Embracing Individualism, Espousing Equity: How Competing Conceptions of Equity Animate Teacher Licensure Reforms. *Maya Kaul, University of Pennsylvania; Meghan Comstock, University of Maryland*

Networks of Resistance: How Intermediary Organizations Counter Civil Rights Rollbacks in Education. *Talia S. Leibovitz, University of California - Berkeley; April Weber Hewko, Virginia Commonwealth University; Elizabeth H. DeBray, University of Georgia; Genevieve P. Siegel-Hawley, Virginia Commonwealth University; Janelle T. Scott, University of California - Berkeley; Erica Frankenberg, Pennsylvania State University; Sarah McCollum, University of Georgia; Kathryn A. McDermott,*

University of Massachusetts - Amherst

The Politicization of Protection: Executive Power and OCR's Shifting Role in Safeguarding Trans Students. *Benjamin Leibovitz, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Maggie Paino, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Chair: *Catherine Kramarczuk Voulgarides, Hunter College - CUNY*

93.057-6. Online/Technology (Table 6). Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

How cyberbonding play informs African American collegians' educational journey map(s) navigation of a southern HBCU. *Bryan Hotchkins, Texas Tech University*

Exploring online course scarcity's impact on college progress: A regression discontinuity approach using waitlist enrollment. *Claire Wladis, Borough of Manhattan Community College; Alyse C. Hachey, University of Texas - El Paso; Christopher H. Rhoads, University of Connecticut; Catherine A. Manly, Fairleigh Dickinson University*

Navigating Digital Gatekeepers: A Scoping Review of Electronic Word-of-Mouth in College Admissions Pathways. *Kayla S. Burt, Massachusetts Institute of Technology*

Chair: *Jimmy Aguilar, University of Southern California*

93.057-7. From Protection to Possibility: Policy, Wellness, and the Making of Safe Spaces in Education (Table 7). Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4;
11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Belonging and Wellness at the Center: Reimagining Schooling in Two Maryland School Districts. *Marina Lambrinou, Loyola University Maryland; Elizabeth Holliday Morgan, Morgan State University; Jessica Shiller, Towson University*

Divided in Space, United in Vision: A Case Study of Partnership In Fugitive Spaces in Politically Divided Times. *Deborah Euzebio, University of Maryland*

From Preference to Policy: How ELCC Type and Satisfaction Shape Parental Psychological Well-being. *Yunqi Xie, University of Toronto - OISE; Samantha Burns, University of Guelph; Esther Yu, University of Toronto - OISE; Jesseca Perlman, University of Toronto - OISE; Michal Perlman, University of Toronto - OISE*

Well-Intentioned, Poorly Enforced: The Hidden Costs of Protective Policies in Schools. *Gilbert Ansah, West Virginia University*

Grading After Reform: How Policy Change Affected Teachers' Grading for University Entrance Qualifications. *Vincent Schatz, University of Vienna; Marko Lüftenegger, Universität Wien*

Chair: *Elizabeth Holliday Morgan, Morgan State University*

93.057-8. Black Feminist Praxis: Freedom Dreaming, Writing, and Storying (Table 8). SIG-Qualitative Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

Sustaining Sisterhood: The Role of Virtual Sister Circles in Mentoring Black Women in Academia During a Dual Pandemic. *Tiffany Hollis, Coastal Carolina University; Tamera D. Moore, Charleston Southern University; Jonimay J. Morgan, Texas A&M University; Jessica R Robinson, University of North Carolina - Charlotte*

Black Feminist Poetic Artful Inquiry as Critical Qualitative Research. *Qiana Cutts Givens, Mississippi State University*
Writing Through Tension: A Black Feminist Reflexive Praxis. *Dana Michelle Harris, Independent Scholar*

Chair: *Amber Pabon, Kutztown University of Pennsylvania*
Discussant: *Evangelina Q. Oates, University of Minnesota*

Division and SIG Posters

93.058. AERA Poster Session Sunday 11:45 am; Poster Session

93.058-1. Deconstructing Whiteness in Teacher Education.

Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Poster:

1. Deconstructing Whiteness in Teacher Education: (Poster 1). *Allison DeVoe Karcher, Siena College*

93.058-2. The Embedding of DEIA in Faculty Evaluations and Tenure Review in California Community Colleges.

Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Poster:

2. The Embedding of DEIA in Faculty Evaluations and Tenure Review in California Community Colleges (Poster 2). *Kristin Lui-Martinez, Loyola Marymount University*

93.058-3. Constructing Early Childhood Education: Ideologies, Influences, and Discourses. SIG-Critical Perspectives on Early Childhood Education; Poster Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Posters:

3. Examining Head Start Funding Equity and Program Quality

Across States (Poster 3). *Allison Boyle, Southern Education Foundation, Inc.; Max Altman, Southern Education Foundation; Kathy Thornburg, University of Missouri; Cathy Grace, University of Mississippi*

4. Health as A Cultural Discourse of Difference: Making the “Disadvantaged Child” (Poster 4). *Xue Yin, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

5. How Are Children Researched and Framed? Disentangling the Deficit-Based Web of Theory, Problematizing, and Interventions in Early Childhood Special Education Research (Poster 5). *Ruby Batz, University of Nevada - Reno; Courtney O’Grady, University of Alabama; Megan Vinh; Asha Yadav, University of Oregon*

6. In Their Own Words: Centering Infant/Toddler Teachers’ Voices on Turnover and Retention (Poster 6). *Christina E Laney, California State University - Long Beach*

7. Mapping American Fascist Tendencies and Antifascist Responsibility in Early Childhood Education (Poster 7). *Katie Sloan, Oakland University*

8. Navigating ECE Advocacy in Precarious Times: Equity Rhetoric and Digital Silence during the 2024 Election (Poster 8). *Shana E. DeVlieger, NYU; Seth Badu, New York University; Fabienne Doucet, New York University*

9. Roosters, Rivalries, and Relational Bonds: Translingual Children’s Stories as Intergenerational Gifts to Multilingual Children (Poster 9). *Youmna Deiri, Texas A&M International University; Ximena Vidal, Texas A&M International University*

10. Strengthening Systems Through Leadership: A Virtual Professional Development Model for Early Intervention (Poster 10). *Savannah Hobbs, University of Denver; Rashida Banerjee, University of Denver; Alissa Rausch, University of Denver; Rachel Anna Kamnkhwani-Kaulembe, Boise State University; Analisa Martinez-Morris, Aurora Public School*

11. Teaching Civil Rights and Responsibilities to Bilingual Kindergarteners through the Home-School Connection (Poster 11). *So Jung Kim, University of Hawai’i at Manoa*

12. Textbook time travel: Narratives of progress and omission in early childhood education histories (Poster 12). *Carolyn Brennan, Western Washington University; Charlene Montano Nolan, Western Washington University*

13. Transitional Kindergarten Expansion and School Segregation: District Perspectives and Policy Landscape Analysis (Poster 13). *Karen Manship, American Institutes for Research; Austin Gragson, North Carolina State University; Noli Brazil, University of California - Davis; Michael Middleton, University of California - Davis*

93.058-4. Making Learning Work: Design and Technology.

SIG-Design and Technology; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Posters:

14. Examining teachers’ perceptions of their uptake and

sustainable use of gamification in formal English language education (Poster 14). *Shen Qiao, The Education University of Hong Kong; Ruoqi Chen, Education University of Hong Kong*

15. From Turns to Trajectories: Sequential Analytics of AI-Generated Student Discourse and Teacher Feedback in a 3D Teacher Simulation (Poster 15). *Jewoong Moon, University of Alabama; Jieun Lim, Daegu National University of Education; Yunseo Lee, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Gyuri Byun, Seoul National University; Yeil Jeong, Seoul National University; Unggi Lee, Korea University*
16. Revisiting the Effectiveness of Virtual Reality for Construction Safety Training: A Bayesian Meta-Analysis (Poster 16). *Jewoong Moon, University of Alabama; Idowu David Awoyemi, University of Alabama*
17. The Future of the Field IS Design (+X) (Poster 17). *Ahmed Lachheb, University of Kansas; Victoria Abramenko-Lachheb, University of Michigan*
18. Pathways to Learning Computer Science: Exploring High School Students' Learning of AI-Powered Educational Robotics (Poster 18). *Gözde McLaughlin, Kent State University; Elena Novak, Kent State University; Sima Ahmadi, Kent State University; Jian Li, Kent State University; Yibei Guo, Kent State University; Rui Liu, Kent State University; Lisa A. Borgerding, Kent State University*

93.058-5. Early Education and Child Development. SIG-Early Education and Child Development; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Posters:

19. Excluded Too Early: Family Perspectives on Early Childhood Program Access for Infants and Toddlers with Special Needs (Poster 19). *Sara Movahedazarhouli*
20. Teacher Turnover Pathways: Linking Classroom Chaos, Job Demands, Executive Functioning Difficulties, Well-being, and Turnover Intention (Poster 20). *Prabhath Palle Waththage, University of Missouri; Uma Awasthi, University of Missouri; Vrushali Gadkari, University of Missouri; Aileen Garcia, University of Missouri; Shinyoung Jeon, University of Missouri*
21. Understanding Digital Technology Use in Early Childhood Classrooms: Insights from a Cross-National Study (Poster 21). *Shuolin He, University of Sheffield*
22. From Passive Mediators to Active Guides: Understanding Chinese Parents' Role in Preschoolers' TikTok Consumption (Poster 22). *Dandan Wu, The Education University of Hong Kong; Eva Yi Hung Lau, Education University of Hong Kong; Zhaotianqin Zhang, The Education University of Hong Kong; Yushu Luo, The Education University of Hong Kong; Clara Yun Nga Choy, The Education University of Hong Kong*
23. Screen time and preschoolers' social-emotional profiles:

The mediating role of parenting stress (Poster 23). *Fa Zhang, Open University of China; Yuyan Xia, University of Kentucky; Chin-Chih Chen, Virginia Commonwealth University; Yaoying Xu, Virginia Commonwealth University; Jamie L. Cage, Virginia Commonwealth University*

24. Navigating AI-Driven Risks in Early Childhood Education Research: A Methodological Reflection on Fraudulent Participation (Poster 24). *Timea Chen, University of Northern Iowa; Wu-Ying Hsieh, University of Northern Iowa; Sohyun Meacham, University of Northern Iowa*
25. Resilience in Diaspora: Using ADDIE to Design and Implement a Resilience Program in Circassian Community (Poster 25). *Aysegul Cetin, TED University; Bilge Uyanik-Koc, Ministry of National Education Turkiye*

93.058-6. Faculty Teaching, Evaluation, and Development.

SIG-Faculty Teaching, Evaluation, and Development; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Posters:

26. Attitude of Faculty towards Multimedia Authoring Tools (Poster 26). *Ebenezer Sanya Ibrinke, University of Ilorin; Deborah Moyaki, University of Georgia; Ayobami Dunmoye, Morgan State University; Isaac Dunmoye, University of Georgia; Nathaniel Hunsu, University of Georgia*
27. Development and Validation of Faculty Research Competence Test: A Cross-Analysis Using CTT and IRT (Poster 27). *Muhammad Salahuddin, University of North Dakota; Robert H. Stupnisky, University of North Dakota*
28. Enhancing Inclusion and Equity in STEM: An Observational Resource Guide for Faculty Professional Development (Poster 28). *Pheather R. Harris, University of California - Irvine; Jacqueline G Cavazos, University of California - Irvine; Tayloria N.G. Adams, University of California - Irvine; Emily A. Affolter, Prescott College*
29. Qualitative Results from the Inaugural Year of an Academy of Medical Educators (Poster 29). *Monica B. Glina, New York Medical College*
30. Validating STEM Faculty Self-reported Research Success with Web of Science Bibliometrics (Poster 30). *Zachary Mark Schultz, University of North Dakota; Muhammad Salahuddin, University of North Dakota; Godwin Ahiase, University of North Dakota; Robert H. Stupnisky, University of North Dakota*

93.058-7. Technology, Instruction, Cognition, and Learning
SIG Poster Session. SIG-Technology, Instruction, Cognition & Learning; Poster Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Posters:

31. Collaborative Learning with Generative AI: A Dual-Layer Metacognitive Scaffolding Framework for Developing

- Hybrid Intelligence (Poster 31). *Miao Yue, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Lillian Wenxuan Liu, University of California - Irvine; Lap Kwan Alex LAM, The Education University of Hong Kong; Morris Siu-Yung Jong, Chinese University of Hong Kong*
32. Empowering Non-Chinese Speaking Students through AI-Driven Real-Life Scenarios in Cantonese (Poster 32). *Ka Yan Fung, The Education University of Hong Kong; Kwong Chiu Fung, Hong Kong University of Science and Technology; Yuxing Tao, The Education University of Hong Kong; Tze Leung Lui, The Education University of Hong Kong; Kuen Fung Kenneth Sin, The Education University of Hong Kong*
33. Exploring Students' Self-Regulated Learning with AI: Preliminary Results from Video Analysis and Process Mining (Poster 33). *Yanxiong Xiang, The Education University of Hong Kong 香港教育大学, Lingyun Huang, The Education University of Hong Kong*
34. Fast But Not Ready: Issues and Results from Using ChatGPT to Grade Essays from Chinese ESL Undergraduates (Poster 34). *Tony Xing Tan, University of South Florida; Blanca Solis, University of South Florida*
35. Meta-Analyses of Artificial Intelligence in K–12 Education: A Review of Reviews (2020–2025) (Poster 35). *Eun Hye Grace Ko, Texas A&M University; Hector H. Rivera, Texas A&M University; Yiming Zhu, Texas A&M University*
36. Self-efficacy mediates but does not moderate the relationship between facilitating conditions and intention to teach English with AI (Poster 36). *Jiajing LI, Beijing Normal University; Yao Zhao, UNC Charlotte; YaoYao Ji, Chinese University of Hong Kong*
37. Teachers-Generative AI Collaboration in Developing Learning Tasks: Mapping the Challenges (Poster 37). *Jie Cao, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Shuman Wang, Stanford University; Christian D. Schunn, University of Pittsburgh*
38. The Cognitive Costs of Mobile Use in Childhood and Adolescence (Poster 38). *Gyongyver Molnar, University of Szeged*
39. Exploring the effects of adaptive gamification on learning motivation (Poster 39). *Shurui Bai, The Education University of Hong Kong; Timothy Khe Foon Hew, University of Hong Kong; Michael Sailer, Learning Analytics and Educational Data Mining; Tyrone Tai On Kwok, Hong Kong Metropolitan University; Zhihao Cui, The Education University of Hong Kong*
40. ChatGPT in Higher Education: A Systematic Review Informed by the Technology Acceptance Model (Poster 40). *Fan Yang, University of Georgia*
41. Clustering Pre-Service Teachers' Reflections on Generative AI: Linguistic, Semantic, and Emotional Trajectories in Online Discussions (Poster 41). *Jaesung Hur, Florida State University; Jewoong Moon, University of Alabama; Gi Woong Choi, Florida State University; Haesol Bae, University at Albany - SUNY; Jaesung Park, University at Albany - SUNY*
- 93.058-8. SIG-RME Poster Session: Explorations of the Mathematics Teaching and Learning Experience.** SIG-Research in Mathematics Education; Poster Session Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 11:45am to 1:15pm
- Posters:
42. An Investigation of the Importance and Usefulness of School Mathematics in the Workplace (Poster 42). *Jonathan Isaac, Southern Methodist University; Candace A. Walkington, Southern Methodist University*
43. Automated Error Classification and Analysis of Fraction Computation Leveraging Large Language Model (Poster 43). *Isha Patil, California State University Los Angeles; Lexi Hwang, California State University - Los Angeles; Ken-ichi Nomura, University of Southern California; Kyle Chasen Hay, University of California - Los Angeles*
44. Claiming Creativity (Poster 44). *Angelina Bisson, University of California - San Diego*
45. Does “Math Identity” Matter? Predictions of STEM Major Intention from HSLS:09 Using Logistic Regression (Poster 45). *Alexis Daniels, Johns Hopkins University*
46. Fidelity in Mathematics Intervention Implementation Research: Lessons from Implementation Science and the Current Practices (Poster 46). *Jingyuan Zhang, East Tennessee State University*
47. Fostering Mathematical Creativity, Content Knowledge, and Pedagogical Content Knowledge through Generative AI-Driven Creativity-Directed Professional Development (Poster 47). *Ali Bicer, Texas A&M University; Tugce Aldemir, Texas A&M University; Micayla Gooden, Texas A&M University; Aysenur Bicer, Texas A&M University; Fay S. Quiroz, University of Wyoming*
48. From Deficit to Strength: How Frame Shifting Transforms Teacher Noticing in Mathematics Education (Poster 48). *Thorsten Scheiner, Australian Catholic University*
49. Homework Time and Quality Matter: Interactive Effects on Mathematics Achievement and Interest (Poster 49). *Kexin Qin, Beijing Normal University; Wang Yehui, Beijing Normal University*
50. How Lesson Design Functions as the Making of an Argument (Poster 50). *Soobin Jeon, University of Michigan; Ruya Savuran, University of Michigan; Amanda Marie Milewski, University of Michigan; Patricio G. Herbst, University of Michigan*
51. Intersections of Inquiry: Analyzing the Referencing of Special Education Research in Mathematics Education Journals (Poster 51). *Sarah A. van Ingen Lauer, University of South Florida; David H. Allsopp, University of South Florida; Krysta Salvato-Hayes, University of South Florida - Tampa; Katherine Nash, University of South Florida - Tampa; Gabriel Oduro-Boamah, University of South Florida*

- Tampa

52. The Use of Customized GenAI Chatbots to Support Preservice Teachers' Understanding of Collective Mathematical Argumentation (Poster 52). *Yuling Zhuang, Texas A&M University; Xiangquan Yao, Pennsylvania State University; Trina J. Davis, Texas A&M University; Wisdom Yao Nudze, Texas A&M University*
53. What the Hex(agon)?: Investigating Preschoolers' Spatial Reasoning Within a Challenging Shape Puzzle (Poster 53). *Emily Perkins, San Diego State University; Nicholas C. Johnson, San Diego State University; Carlos Alejandro de Alba, San Diego State University*

93.059. e-Lightning Ed-Talk Session 22 - Stage 1. AERA e-Lightning Ed-Talks; AERA Ed Talk
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Exhibit Hall A
- Stage 1; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

- The Embedding of DEIA in Faculty Evaluations and Tenure Review in California Community Colleges (Stage 1, 11:50 AM). *Kristin Lui-Martinez, Loyola Marymount University*
- Strengthening Systems Through Leadership: A Virtual Professional Development Model for Early Intervention (Stage 1, 11:59 AM). *Savannah Hobbs, University of Denver; Rashida Banerjee, University of Denver; Alissa Rausch, University of Denver; Rachel Anna Kamnkhwani-Kaulembe, Boise State University; Analisa Martinez-Morris, Aurora Public School*
- Roosters, Rivalries, and Relational Bonds: Translingual Children's Stories as Intergenerational Gifts to Multilingual Children (Stage 1, 12:08 PM). *Youmna Deiri, Texas A&M International University; Ximena Vidal, Texas A&M International University*
- How Are Children Researched and Framed? Disentangling the Deficit-Based Web of Theory, Problematizing, and Interventions in Early Childhood Special Education Research (Stage 1, 12:17 PM). *Ruby Batz, University of Nevada - Reno; Courtney O'Grady, University of Alabama; Megan Vinh; Asha Yadav, University of Oregon*
- Examining Head Start Funding Equity and Program Quality Across States (Stage 1, 12:26 PM). *Allison Boyle, Southern Education Foundation, Inc.; Max Altman, Southern Education Foundation; Kathy Thornburg, University of Missouri; Cathy Grace, University of Mississippi*
- Pathways to Learning Computer Science: Exploring High School Students' Learning of AI-Powered Educational Robotics (Stage 1, 12:35 PM). *Gözde McLaughlin, Kent State University; Elena Novak, Kent State University; Sima Ahmadi, Kent State University; Jian Li, Kent State University; Yibei Guo, Kent State University; Rui Liu, Kent State University; Lisa A. Borgerding, Kent State University*
- Understanding Digital Technology Use in Early Childhood Classrooms: Insights from a Cross-National Study (Stage 1, 12:50 PM). *Shuolin He, University of Sheffield*

Qualitative Results from the Inaugural Year of an Academy of Medical Educators (Stage 1, 1:08 PM). *Monica B. Glina, New York Medical College*

93.060. e-Lightning Ed-Talk Session 22 - Stage 2. AERA e-Lightning Ed-Talks; AERA Ed Talk
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Exhibit Hall A
- Stage 2; 11:45am to 1:15pm

Participants:

- Automated Error Classification and Analysis of Fraction Computation Leveraging Large Language Model (Stage 2, 11:50 AM). *Isha Patil, California State University Los Angeles; Lexi Hwang, California State University - Los Angeles; Ken-ichi Nomura, University of Southern California; Kyle Chasen Hay, University of California - Los Angeles*
- An Investigation of the Importance and Usefulness of School Mathematics in the Workplace (Stage 2, 11:59 AM). *Jonathan Isaac, Southern Methodist University; Candace A. Walkington, Southern Methodist University*
- Collaborative Learning with Generative AI: A Dual-Layer Metacognitive Scaffolding Framework for Developing Hybrid Intelligence (Stage 2, 12:08 PM). *Miao Yue, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Lillian Wenxuan Liu, University of California - Irvine; Lap Kwan Alex LAM, The Education University of Hong Kong; Morris Siu-Yung Jong, Chinese University of Hong Kong*
- Exploring Students' Self-Regulated Learning with AI: Preliminary Results from Video Analysis and Process Mining (Stage 2, 12:17 PM). *Yanxiong Xiang, The Education University of Hong Kong 香港教育大学; Lingyun Huang, The Education University of Hong Kong*
- Fast But Not Ready: Issues and Results from Using ChatGPT to Grade Essays from Chinese ESL Undergraduates (Stage 2, 12:26 PM). *Tony Xing Tan, University of South Florida; Blanca Solis, University of South Florida*
- Meta-Analyses of Artificial Intelligence in K-12 Education: A Review of Reviews (2020-2025) (Stage 2, 12:35 PM). *Eun Hye Grace Ko, Texas A&M University; Hector H. Rivera, Texas A&M University; Yiming Zhu, Texas A&M University*
- The Cognitive Costs of Mobile Use in Childhood and Adolescence (Stage 2, 12:50 PM). *Gyongyver Molnar, University of Szeged*
- Exploring the effects of adaptive gamification on learning motivation (Stage 2, 12:59 PM). *Shurui Bai, The Education University of Hong Kong; Timothy Khe Foon Hew, University of Hong Kong; Michael Sailer, Learning Analytics and Educational Data Mining; Tyrone Tai On Kwok, Hong Kong Metropolitan University; Zhihao Cui, The Education University of Hong Kong*
- Chair: *Steven Andrew Culpepper, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Sunday, April 12th, 1:45 pm

Committee Sessions

94.010. Graduate Student–Led Research Conferences as Sites of Past, Present, and Future Dialogue in Education Research.

Graduate Student Council; Invited Speaker Session

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 402A; 1:45-3:15pm

Chair: *Marjorie M. Hahn, Stanford University*

Panelists: *Gabriela López, Stanford University; Melissa Lewis, Stanford University; Marcos Rojas, Stanford University; Carolyn Oei, University of Toronto - OISE*

Division Sessions

94.011. The Institutionalization of K-12 Ethnic Studies: Implementing Innovative Curricula across Diverse Social and Political Contexts.

Division B - Curriculum Studies; Symposium

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304A; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Precarious Possibilities: One School District's Effort to Institutionalize Critical Ethnic Studies. *Kysa Nygreen, University of Massachusetts - Amherst; Joel A. Arce, University of Massachusetts Amherst; Dana Altshuler, University of Massachusetts - Amherst; Keisha L. Green, University of Massachusetts - Amherst; Laura A. Valdiviezo, University of Massachusetts - Amherst*

Mandating an Elective? The Implementation of Black and Latino Studies Courses in Connecticut High Schools. *Hannah Cooke, University of Connecticut; Alexandra J. Freidus, University of Connecticut; Janak Raj Pant, University of Connecticut*

Ethnic Studies Without Ethnic Studies Pedagogy?: Mandating the Teaching of Ethnic Studies in Connecticut. *Jia-Hui Stefanie Wong, Trinity College*

Ethnic Studies Teachers as Policymakers: Imagining Ethnic Studies for Multilingual Newcomer Immigrant Youth in California. *Rita Kamani-Renedo, Stanford University; Eujin Park, Stanford University*

Chair: *Jia-Hui Stefanie Wong, Trinity College*

Discussant: *Alexandra J. Freidus, University of Connecticut*

94.012. (Re)membering, (Re)cognizing, and Responsibility: How Cynthia Dillard's Work Helps Us Meet the Current Moment.

Division G - Social Context of Education; Symposium

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 301B;

1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

The Spirit of Her Work: Dr. Cynthia Dillard & Responsibility. *Bettina L. Love, Teachers College, Columbia University*

I Am Because She Is: Epistemological Permission through Endarkened Knowledge-Ways. *Stephanie R. Toliver, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Three Consequential Moments and Movements of Cynthia Dillard's Work. *Rich Milner, Vanderbilt University*

Teaching next to the wound: Pedagogies, curriculum, and engaging racialized trauma through (re)membering. *Stephanie P. Jones, Grinnell College*

Dr. Cynthia Dillard's Call to (Re)member: Aligning K-12 Education with Our Ancestral Knowing and Queen Being. *Damaris C. Dunn, Drexel University; Yaribel Mercedes, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Endarkened Feminist Epistemology as Balm and Blueprint: The Enduring Influence of Dr. Cynthia B. Dillard on Educational Research and Praxis. *Terah J. Stewart, Iowa State University*

Chair: *Kristen Duncan, Clemson University*

Discussants: *Amber Neal-Stanley, Purdue University; Cynthia B. Dillard, Seattle University*

94.013. Dare Everything: Love Letters to Educational Leaders During an Era of 47.

Division G - Social Context of Education; Symposium

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 303B; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

The Fire Is Now: Love Letter to Educational Leaders. *G.T. Reyes, California State University - East Bay*

Light the Fire, Light the Way: Love Letter to Educational Leaders. *Pedro E. Nava, Santa Clara University*

The Good Fire Now: Love Letter to Educational Leaders. *Orlando L. Carreón, Sonoma State University*

Chair: *Orlando L. Carreón, Sonoma State University*

Discussant: *Dolores Delgado Bernal, Loyola Marymount University*

94.014. Unsilencing the Past, Regifting the Present, and Manifesting Unforgettable Futures: Multiliteracies, Entertainment, and Popular Culture.

Division G - Social Context of Education; Symposium

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 303A; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Experiences with Futures Scenario Planning and Arts-Based Educational Approaches in an Undergraduate Education Course. *Darnel Degand, University of California - Davis*

Ctrl+Alt+Resist: Digital protest and speculative activism in videogaming ecologies. *Arturo Cortez, University of California - Davis*

Play, Narrative, and Belonging in STEM Media: Centering Black Boys' Imaginations. *Kareem Edouard, Drexel*

University

Speculative Fabulation and Algorithmic Resistance in Queer and Latinx Community-based AI Workshops. *José Ramón Lizárraga, University of Colorado - Boulder*

Chair: *Darnel Degand, University of California - Davis*

Discussant: *Kris D. Gutiérrez, University of California - Berkeley*

94.015. Latiné/x Students: Experiences, Growth, and

Servingness Across Contexts. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum F; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Centering Cultural Wealth: Undergraduate Identity Development in a Summer Research Program at an HSI. *Anissa R. Stewart, University of California - Santa Barbara; Fátima Andrade Martínez, University of California - Santa Barbara; Lupita Romo-González, University of California - Santa Barbara*

Faith, Family, and Failure? Guilt, Shame, and Academic Recovery among Latina Undergraduates on Probation. *Mary Dueñas, University of Tennessee; Lazaro Camacho, University of Rhode Island; Pietro Antonio Sasso, Delaware State University*

Navigating Industry, Shaping Identity: Latina Engineering Students' Cultural Capital in Work-Integrated Learning Experiences. *Alice Eunjung Lee, University of Texas - El Paso*

Relational Roots of Character: Centering Student Voices and Faculty Impact at a Hispanic-Serving Institution. *Anglin Thevaraja, Montclair State University; Elaine Les, Montclair State University; Yasmine Perry, Montclair State University; Elyse L. Postlewaite, Montclair State University; Miriam Linver, Montclair State University*

Chair: *Cristina Nader, Texas A&M University*

94.016. Mapping Racial Projects in Postsecondary STEM:

Interrogating Scripts, Schemas, and Structures for Justice. Division J - Postsecondary Education; Symposium JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum H; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

De-homogenizing 'Asian Americans' in Physics Education: DesiCrit as an Analytic Framework. *Tra Huynh, Western Washington University; Amy Robertson, Seattle Pacific University; Shahnaz Masani, Michigan State University*

Engineering Education Reinforces Monolithic Constructions of Latino/a/e/x Identity and Stifles Critical Consciousness. *Summer Rose Blanco, University of Georgia; Tatiane Russo-Tait, University of Georgia*

Developing Learning Assistants' Critical Consciousness and Racial Noticing Lens through a Justice-Oriented STEM Fellowship. *Regan Levy, Michigan State University; Shahnaz Masani, Michigan State University*

How Students from Different Racial Backgrounds Enact and Resist Racial Scripts in Peer Discussion. *Hannah Nichols, University of Georgia; Tatiane Russo-Tait, University of Georgia; Lauryn Famble, University of Georgia*

Mapping the Racialized Organization of STEM Academic Departments. *Meaghan Pearson, Vanderbilt University; Aireale J. Rodgers, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Tatiane Russo-Tait, University of Georgia*

Chair: *Tatiane Russo-Tait, University of Georgia*

Discussant: *Terrell R Morton, University of Illinois at Chicago*

94.017. We Wrote Ourselves In: The Doctoral Student Writing Collective as a Blueprint for Belonging. Division J -

Postsecondary Education; Symposium JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum G; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Collective Words, Collective Healing: The Role of Writing Groups in Fostering Community and Belonging for Black Doctoral Students. *Da'Ja'Nay Askew, Indiana University; Tim Herd, University of California - Los Angeles*

Writing Together: Fostering Belonging for Black Doctoral Students. *Da'Ja'Nay Askew, Indiana University; Tim Herd, University of California - Los Angeles*

Haunting the Ivory Tower: Academic Trauma, Blackness, and the Future of Doctoral Education. *Da'Ja'Nay Askew, Indiana University; Tim Herd, University of California - Los Angeles*

Chair: *Da'Ja'Nay Askew, Indiana University*

Discussant: *Tim Herd, University of California - Los Angeles*

94.018. Advocacy, Community, and Transformative Practice in Education. Division K - Teaching and Teacher

Education; Paper Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 6; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Cultivating Critical Transformative Teacher Agency through Co-Design with Families toward Climate Justice. *Wisam Sedawi, University of Michigan; Angela Calabrese, University of Michigan; Batoul Abdallah, University of Michigan; Rachel Sherwin, University of Michigan*

Education Brokering: School Personnel's Efforts to Support and Educate Newcomer Immigrant Students under Conditions of Constraint. *Carolyn Sattin-Bajaj, University of California - Santa Barbara; Marie R Fernandez, University of California - Santa Barbara*

Mapping Book Banning Resistance: Visualizing Teacher and Youth-Led Acts of Advocacy in an Era of Censorship. *Jason Griffith, Pennsylvania State University; Stephanie F. Reid, University of Cincinnati*

The roots of teachers' critical advocacy for multilingual learners: Connecting personal histories to action. *Rebecca E. Linares, Rowan University; Kate Seltzer, Rowan University*

Teacher Activists and Social Movements: How Social

Movement Learning Translates into Pedagogical Practice.
Jennifer Queenan, Graduate Center - CUNY

Chair: *Andrea E. Weinberg, Arizona State University*

Discussant: *Michelle Jordan, Arizona State University*

94.019. AI in Teacher Preparation: Exploring Literacy, Lesson Planning, and Collaborative Practices. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 8; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

AI Integration in Early Childhood Education: Perspectives and Imagining Futures from Pre-service Teachers. *Zhuoyun Cai, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

AI-TPACK in Action: How Preservice Teachers Use GenAI Tools for Lesson Planning. *Yuxia Peng, Moansh University; Sun Yee Yip, Monash University*

Exploring AI Use in Instructional Planning: Voices of Early Childhood Pre-Service Teachers. *Jaehee Kwon, SUNY at Fredonia; Sung Eun Jung, University of Arizona*

What a difference a year makes: Comparing PSTs' use of GenAI in 2024 vs. 2025. *Jennifer E. Lineback, Point Loma Nazarene University; Elizabeth Holbrook, Point Loma Nazarene University*

Chair: *Keirah Comstock, University of Rochester*

Discussant: *Shalaunda M. Reeves, University of Tennessee*

94.020. Exploring the Evolution of Professional Learning Communities Within Chinese Cultural Contexts. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 9; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Beyond Silence: Exploring Chinese Preschool Teachers' Emotional Experiences in an Emotion-focused Professional Development Program. *Jiaxuan Lian, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Yitong Jiang, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Hongbiao Yin, The Chinese University of Hong Kong*

Early childhood teachers' learning in professional learning communities: A case study in Mainland China. *Han QIN, Capital Normal University; Hongbiao Yin, The Chinese University of Hong Kong*

From Text to Context: How Teachers Collaboratively Construct Subject Didactic Knowledge for Classical Chinese Instruction. *Yu-Ting Hung, National Taipei University of Education*

Mentoring Teacher Leaders through Networked Professional Learning Communities: A case from from China. *Chenya Wang, East China Normal University; Zheng Xin, East China Normal University*

Chair: *Rosie Ojeda, California Polytechnic State University - San Luis Obispo*

Discussant: *Jenny Tuten, Hunter College - CUNY*

94.021. Looking Back, Envisioning Forward: Teacher Educators of Color Unsettling Whiteness for Collective Liberation. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 1; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Telling the Truth: Critical Race Theory, Teacher Preparation, and the Urgency of (Re)membering Anti-Racist Education. *Cleveland Hayes, Indiana University - Indianapolis*

Unforgetting the Emotionalities of Whiteness: Rectifying the Racial Harms in Teacher Education. *Cheryl E. Matias, University of San Diego*

Leveraging Relationships in Pursuit of Racially-Just, Culturally Sustaining Teacher Diversification Pathways in the Midwest. *Amanda Morales, University of Nebraska - Lincoln*

Critical Family History as a Gateway to Racial Literacy in Teacher Education. *Lin Wu, Western Oregon University*

Chair: *Kimberly A. White-Smith, University of San Diego*

Discussant: *Dorinda Carter Andrews, Michigan State University*

94.022. Making Teachers, Making Knowledge: Professionalism, Partnerships, and the Politics of Evidence. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 2; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Are Teachers Professionals? An Enduring Question in an Era of Polarization. *Emilie Mitescu Reagan, Claremont Graduate University; A. Lin Goodwin, Boston College*

From Semantic Topics to Structural Dimensions in Teacher Education: A BERTopic Model. *CHUANG YANG, Guangzhou University; Qi Xiu, South China Normal University*

On the Organization of Research Communication and Knowledge Production in Teacher Education Research. *Sverker Lindblad, Gothenburg University; Gustaf Nelhans, University of Borås; Katarina Samuelsson, Gothenburg University*

Partnerships As Levers in Teacher Education Policy. *Henning Fjortoft, Norwegian University of Science and Technology; Tine Sophie Prøitz, University of South-Eastern Norway; Andreas Lund, University of Oslo*

94.023. Radical Acts of Care in Teaching. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 7; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Exploring Teacher Care Labor and Possibilities for Just Care.

Marie R Fernandez, University of California - Santa Barbara

Politicized Care: Marginalized Teachers' Justice-Oriented Relationship Building with Students. *Ji Y. Hong, University of Arizona; Qian Wang, University of Oklahoma; Dionne Cross Francis, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*

Teachers' Experiences of Pumping at Work: Centering Outlaw Emotions. *Elise Toedt, University of Minnesota*

Unforgetting Burnout: Reimagining Teacher Identity, Meaning, and Well-being in Agricultural Education. *Kenny Chio Saephan, The Ohio State University; Amanda Michelle Bowling, The Ohio State University*

Chair: Marie R Fernandez, University of California - Santa Barbara

Discussant: Malayna Bernstein, University of Toronto

94.024. Politics, History, and Systems Improvement in 21st Century School Reforms. Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 4th Floor, Diamond 10; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Educational System Building in the Shadow of History: Race, Control, Politics, and School Reform. *William Berry, The George Washington University*

From Accountability to Algorithms: Interorganizational Struggle and the Transformation of Chicago's Dropout Prevention System. *Jose Eos Trinidad, University of California - Berkeley*

Looking Across Evidence Sources for Patterns in the U.S. K-12 School System Improvement Literature. *Beth Schueler, University of Virginia*

Critical Perspectives on the Contexts of Improvement-Focused Educational Research. *Huriya Jabbar, University of Southern California; Joshua Childs, University of Texas at Austin*

Politics at the Boundary: Continuing to Explore Politics in Education Research-Practice Partnerships. *Kyo Yamashiro, Loyola Marymount University; Laura P. Wentworth, California Education Partners; Moonhawk Kim, University of California - Berkeley*

Chair: Joshua L. Glazer, The George Washington University

Discussant: Donald J. Peurach, University of Michigan

94.025. Unforgetting Punishment: How Safety Policies Reproduce—or Resist—Inequity in Schools. Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum I; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Framing School Securitization: A Qualitative Policy Analysis of the School Violence Prevention Program. *Sidra Sheikh, The Center for Program Design and Evaluation*

Reimagining School Safety Through Participatory Governance:

Power, History, and Policy in Chicago Public Schools.

David Wilson Johnson, Northwestern University; Christina Scanlon, University of Chicago; Joseph Hoereth, University of Illinois at Chicago

School Stakeholders' Acceptance of School Security Technologies. *Abigail J. Beneke, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Samantha L. Viano, George Mason University; Catalina Valdez, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Benjamin W. Fisher, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Alyssa Barone, George Mason University*

Understanding Corporal Punishment Policy in Mississippi and Alabama: A Critical Discourse Analysis. *Gariel Pierce, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Chair: Samantha L. Viano, George Mason University

Discussant: Chris Curran, University of Florida

SIG Sessions

94.026. Centering Relationality & Expanding Knowledge through Artistic Practice: Transdisciplinary Education Research and Arts Methodologies for Change. SIG-Arts-Based Educational Research; Symposium
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 304B; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Collaborative Portraits: Extending Indigenous Storytelling Research Practices Beyond Text. *Jarita Greyeyes, McMaster University*

Feeling the data: Mirrored Invitations to Make, Listen and See Educational Possibility. *Melita Morales, School of the Art Institute of Chicago; Shirin Vossoughi, Northwestern University; Sam Carroll, McGaw YMCA; Onam Lansana, Northwestern University*

Letters to Lab Rats and Stories of Magical Stardust; Storying as Relationally Mediated Artistic Practice. *Meg Elena Escudé, University of California - Berkeley; Jorge Eduardo Garcia, Stanford University*

Storying Relationships in the Language Classroom. *Alex Mejía, San Francisco State University; Cristina Selena Mendez, University of California - Berkeley*

Convivencia as a Fandango Design Principle: Developing Community-led Son Jarocho Workshops. *Yared Portillo, University of California - Berkeley*

Arts, Crafts, and Analytic Collage: Insights from Relating Community Members' Artistic Creations Via Collage. *Melissa Perez, University of Michigan*

Chair: Meg Elena Escudé, University of California - Berkeley
Discussant: Ananda M. Marin, University of California - Los Angeles

94.027. Formative Interventions from the Global South: Expansive Learning as Justice-Oriented Educational Praxis. SIG-Cultural-Historical Research; Symposium

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Los Feliz; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Research as Kin-making: Expansive Learning through Indigenous and Ecological Praxis. *Aydin Bal, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Inny Accioly, Universidade Federal Fluminense*

Re-mediating Practices: A Journey of Culturally Responsive Formative Intervention. *Fabiane Bravo M. Bastos, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Angelica Bêta, Instituto Benjamin Constant; Fabiana Rangel, Instituto Benjamin Constant; Ivan Finamore, Instituto Benjamin Constant; Karine Pereira, Instituto Benjamin Constant*

Transforming Teaching Research Activities through a Change Laboratory Intervention in China. *Chunting Diao, Hubei University of Chinese Medicine; Wei Yue, Central China Normal University*

Collaborative Design of School-Wide Positive Behavioral Interventions and Supports: A Formative Intervention Study in Türkiye. *Kemal Afacan, Artvin Coruh University; Halil Ibrahim Cakir, Giresun University*

Chair: *Aydin Bal, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Discussant: *Fernanda Liberali, Pontificia Universidad Catolica de Sao Paulo*

94.028. Bordering Difference and Reimagining Inclusive

Futures: Global Struggles Toward Intersectional

Justice. SIG-Disability Studies in Education; Symposium

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Room 511AB; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

“The Weight We Carry”: A Teenager Addresses a Violent and Unsupportive Ninth-Grade School Year. *Helena Donato-Sapp, Vistamar School; Erwin Dionisio Donato, Independent Scholar; Jeff Sapp, California State University - Dominguez Hills*

Biopolitics, Debilitation, and Neoliberal Post-Colonialism: Humanism versus Educational Rights for Ukrainian Refugee Children in Ireland. *Nickie Coomer, Colorado College*

Crafting Disabilities: A Critical Examination of Disability Identification for Multicultural Learners in South Korea. *Dosun Ko, Santa Clara University; Yehyang Lee, Syracuse University; Jane Y. Jeong, University of Texas at Austin; Byul Yim, Independent Scholar*

Moving Beyond Borders: Toward Liberatory Possibility in Advanced Education. *Alejandra Amaris Fernández Morgado, Florida International University*

On the Borderlands across Languaculture and Identities: A Critical Autoethnography of a Transnational Filipina’s Journey. *Monaliza M Chian, University of Northern Iowa*

Chair: *Dosun Ko, Santa Clara University*

Discussant: *David I. Hernandez-Saca, University of Northern Iowa*

94.029. Home-school engagement and partnerships. SIG-

Family, School, Community Partnerships; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Plaza III;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Reimagining Family-School Partnerships Amid Societal Changes in Finnish Education. *Isaac McCann, Oklahoma State University; Haley McCray, Oklahoma State University; Starr Holmes, Oklahoma State University; Vanessa Collins, Oklahoma State University; Jentre J. Olsen, Oklahoma State University; Katherine A. Curry, Oklahoma State University*

Partnership Matters: Interwoven Ecological Influences on Children’s Learning Outcomes — A Study from Alabama’s Black Belt. *Yan Dai, Tuskegee University*

Parents’ Perspectives on ‘Good’ versus ‘Bad’ home-school communication practices. *Laura Teichert, Western Michigan University*

(Re)Building Relationships: Family Engagement After a Pandemic. *Aaron Leo, University at Albany - SUNY; Kristen C. Wilcox, University at Albany - SUNY*

“Breaking Down that Barrier of Students and Teachers”: Teacher Perceptions of a Home Visit Program. *Pallavi Chhabra, Washington University in St. Louis; Margaret K. Powers, Washington University in St. Louis; Megumi Grace Hine, Washington University in St. Louis; Katrina Harmon, Lindenwood University*

Chair: *Hui Zhang, University of Toledo*

Discussant: *Kyle Elizabeth Miller, Illinois State University*

94.030. Critical Dialogues in Latinx Education. SIG-Latina/o/x

Research Issues; Symposium

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Plaza II; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

A Broad Politics of Justice: A Practitioner Inquiry Study into Latinidad & Latine/x Education at a College Education Symposium. *Yianella M. Blanco, University of California - Davis; Alicia Rusoja, University of California - Davis; Michael V. Singh, University of California - Davis*

Centering Black Geographies in Latinx Education Scholarship: Youth Perspectives from El Sur Latinx. *Rebeca Gamez, Vanderbilt University*

“It was affirming and beautiful.” Visibilizing the experiences of Central American students and the teachers who teach them. *Floralma Boj Lopez, University of California - Los Angeles; Ron Espiritu, Hacienda La Puente Unified School District; Luis Urrieta, University of Texas at Austin*

A Composite Conversation on Latinx Racialization in Education. *Laura Chavez-Moreno, University of California - Los Angeles; Celia Lacayo, University of California - Los Angeles*

Chair: *Timothy Monreal, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

Discussant: *Timothy Monreal, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

94.031. Critical Media Literacy to Imagine, Empower, and

Transform Educational Research and Practice. SIG-Media, Culture, and Learning; Symposium
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Georgia I;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Teacher Collective Agency, Disciplinary Literacies, and the Praxis of Critical Media Literacy in Teacher/Education. *Noah Asher Golden, California State University - Long Beach*

“We Teach Anyway”: Community-Responsive K-12 Critical Media Literacy Education. *Andrea L. Gambino, University of Southern California*

Critical Media Literacy and the Climate Crisis: Interrogating Ideology and the Politics of Representation. *Jeff Share, University of California - Los Angeles*

Chair: *Douglas Kellner, University of California - Los Angeles*

Discussant: *Amina Humphrey, El Camino College*

94.032. Power as Resource, Tool, and Constraint: Examining Power in Educational Organizations. SIG-Organizational Theory; Symposium

Westin Bonaventure, Lobby Level, Los Cerritos; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Mapping Power in K-12 US Educational Research. *Kemi A. Oyewole, University of Pennsylvania; Angel Xiao Bohannon, NORC at the University of Chicago; Kate Kennedy, University of Cincinnati*

Control+Alt+Delete: Authoritarian Educational Leadership and the State Takeover of Houston ISD. *Daniel Dawer, University of Texas at Austin; Meredith Wronowski, University of Dayton*

‘Betraying Our Educational Mission’: Power, Resistance, and Agency in Israeli-Sponsored Training for East Jerusalem Teachers. *Emily N. Reich, University of California - Berkeley; Samira Alayan, Hebrew University of Jerusalem and David Yellin College of Education*

Different Journeys, Shared Destinations: Power Dynamics in Implementing a Statewide School Board Governance Framework. *Rachel Sue White, University of Texas at Austin*

Power and Politics in Pennsylvania’s Court-Ordered School Finance Reform. *Joshua Bleiberg, University of Pittsburgh; Nell Williams, EdFund; Ai Shao, University of Pittsburgh*

Chair: *Kemi A. Oyewole, University of Pennsylvania*

Discussant: *David H. Eddy-Spicer, University of Virginia*

94.033. Analyzing Policy Through Critical Research Methods.

SIG-Politics of Education; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Plaza I;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Exclusion by Design: American K–12 Parasitic Syndrome and the Racialized Economics of Teacher Tenure. *Jamela Joseph, Howard University*

“Stars Fell [In] Alabama”: Toward a Critical Race Theory Approach to Music Learning and Teaching. *Joyce M. McCall, Arizona State University; Adrienne D. Dixon, Pennsylvania State University*

What Fails, Teaches: On Ungrading, Black Feminist Pedagogy, and the Neoliberal University. *Dana Michelle Harris, Independent Scholar*

Defining Schooling from the Top: Analyzing Trump’s Second Term Executive Orders in K–12 Education. *Danielle R. Brown, Florida Atlantic University; Macie Barrett, Florida Atlantic University*

Chair: *Jawanza Kalonji Rand, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Discussant: *Nathalie Mizelle, University of the District of Columbia*

94.034. Navigating Challenges, Cultivating Strengths: Rural Educational Leadership for Justice and Inclusion. SIG-Rural Education; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 3rd Floor, Georgia II;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Equity in Access to College Readiness Programs in Rural Charter and Traditional Public Schools in the United States. *Ali Jahanaray, Clemson University; Phillip D. Grant, Clemson University*

From Arrival to Graduation: Guatemalan Newcomer Immigrant Adolescents Refashioning Rural High School Enrollment and Retention. *Sophia Piral Lee, University of Missouri*
Market Theory Meets Rural Realities: Rural Superintendent Perceptions of Competition with Cyber Charter Schools. *Karen Eppley, Pennsylvania State University; Matthew G. Kelly, University of Washington; Annie Maselli, U.S. Department of Education*

Place-Based Leadership Pipelines: Centering Rural Contexts in the Development of School Principals. *Amy Price Azano, Virginia Tech; David Kniola, Virginia Tech; Charles L. Lowery, Virginia Tech*

Unforgetting Rural Talent: A Convergent Mixed Methods Study on Equity and Gifted Identification in Underrepresented Communities. *Hosna khorsandi, University of Denver; Kristina Astrid Hesbol, University of Denver; Norma L. Hafenstein, University of Denver; Lindsey Reinert, University of Denver*

Chair: *Kelly S. Hall, Texas A&M University - Kingsville*

Discussant: *Kelly S. Hall, Texas A&M University - Kingsville*

94.035. Transforming Policy for Equity: International Perspectives on Inclusive Multilingual Education. SIG-Second Language Research; Paper Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum A; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Individualized Language Plans: A Content Analysis of English

Language Development Goals. *Sara E.N. Kangas, Lehigh University; Dylan Young, Lehigh University; Xiaodi Li, Lehigh University*

Leaders' Sensemaking for Multilingual Learner Equity: A Case Study. *Nora Turriago, University of California - San Diego*
Policy, Proficiency, and Performance: A Correlational Analysis of State Literacy and English Learner Policies and Their Relationship to NAEP Reading Outcomes. *Heather Elizabeth Lynch, University of Louisiana at Lafayette; Amanda S. Mayeaux, University of Louisiana at Lafayette; Ismatara Reena, University of Louisiana at Lafayette; Nathan M. Roberts, University of Louisiana at Lafayette*
The Impact of Arts and Humanities Instruction on the Development of Receptive Ability of English Learning: A Meta-Analysis. *Jr-An Lin, Texas A&M University; Garion Frankel, Texas A&M University; Lu Chen, Texas A&M University; Yanbing Chen, Texas A&M University; Li-Jen Kuo, Texas A&M University*

Chair: *Hyun-Sook Kang, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Discussant: *Jeff MacSwan, University of Maryland*

94.036. Critical Intersections: Reimagining Race, Disability, Behavior, and Neurodiversity. SIG-Special and Inclusive Education Research; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum J; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Check Yo'self: Culturally Responsive Behavioral Practices for Black Students with Emotional and Behavioral Disorders. *Sharde Theodore, Florida International University; Ayodele Patience Aborishade, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Monica Brown, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*

Introducing a Holistic Framework for Mapping the Needs of Neurodiverse Learners. *Niki Elliott, University of San Diego*

Race, Disability, and Trauma as Predictors of Exclusionary Discipline: Risk and Protective Factors. *Jenny Goldberg, University of California - Santa Barbara; Amber Alaniz, Tanager Place*

Who's on the Page? A Content Analysis of Autism Representation in Children's Picture Books. *Christina Toolan, California State University - Dominguez Hills; Rodrigo Arenas Loma, California State University - Dominguez Hills*

Chair: *Tamara Handy, Teachers College, Columbia University*

94.037. Student Experiences with AI-Assisted Learning. SIG-Technology as an Agent of Change in Teaching and Learning; Paper Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum B; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

How Do Students Collaborate with AI in Problem-Solving Tasks? Unpacking Interaction Profiles and Strategies.

Zhanxin Hao, Tsinghua University; Xiaobo Liu, Tsinghua University; Jiaxin Fan, Tsinghua University; Jifan Yu, Tsinghua University; Yu Zhang, Tsinghua University

Investigating Antecedents of Engagement in GenAI-supported Learning: The Critical Roles of GenAI Competency and Emotion. *Xianhan Huang, The Education University of Hong Kong; Shiyu Zhang, University of Hong Kong; Wen SHAO, University of Hong Kong*

Learning to Program with LLMs: How University Students Use LLMs in an Introductory Programming Course. *Yuwei Liang, University of Pennsylvania; Shiyang Zhang, University of Pennsylvania; Bodong Chen, University of Pennsylvania*

Chair: *Kelly Davis, University of Houston*

Division and SIG Roundtables

94.038. AERA Roundtable Session Sunday 1:45 pm;
Roundtable Session

94.038-1. AI Meets Educational Leadership (Table 1). Division A - Administration; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

AI Implementation Practices and Ethical Considerations of AI Adoption in K-12 Leaders. *Elizabeth Davis, George Mason University; Seth B. Hunter, George Mason University*

Challenging Assumptions: System-Level Leadership of Educational Technology and Generative AI for Equity in Secondary Schools. *Brian R Simmons, University of California - Berkeley*

Co-Occurrence Network Analysis to Guide Responsible AI Policy Development in K-12 Education. *Qurrat-ul-Ain Rasheed, Georgia State University*

Principals as Innovation Brokers in AI Integration Amidst Exam Pressures in China's Periphery. *Ban Wang, HONG KONG UNIVERSITY; Paul Campbell, The University of Hong Kong*

Chair: *Zhaochen Gu, University of Illinois at Chicago*

94.038-2. Culturally Responsive Leadership for Diversity (Table 2). Division A - Administration; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Facilitating Culturally Responsive Change: Learning from Intentionally Diverse Public Charter Schools Leaders. *Karen Michele Drezner, Leveraging Leaders*

Culturally Relevant Leadership in Practice: Navigating Crisis and Student Diversity in Three Chilean Schools. *Maria Eugenia Rojas Concha, Pontificia Universidad Catolica de Valparaiso; Carmen Montecinos, Universidad Catolica de*

Valparaiso; Jorge Rojas, Universidad de Concepción
School Principal Cultural Proficiency and Transformational
Leadership. *Queinnise Miller, University of Houston - Clear
Lake; Rogelio Cardona, University of Houston - Clear Lake*
Chair: *Kendall Dwayne Deas, University of South Carolina*

94.038-3. Agency, Resilience, and Motivation: Strategic Responses to Barriers in Education (Table 3). Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

- Experiences of Foundational Black American Male Faculty in Academia: A Qualitative Black Critical Phenomenology Study. *Mustafaa Muhamed, Jackson College; Belle B. Booker-Zorigian, National University*
- Interconnected Nontraditional Student Characteristics and Resilience: A Strength-Based Analysis. *Sangmin Park, California State University - Sacramento; Sanga Kim, University of Houston*
- The Impact of Language Barriers on Latino Parents' Educational Support. *Brenda Rojas Amarilla, The Ohio State University; Belinda Gimbert, The Ohio State University*
- Voicing through Silence: Relational, Embodied, and Linguistic Agency among American Muslim Girls. *Amal Mahmoud Rizk Elassi, Transylvania University*
- When parental education level matters: Motivating low-SES adolescents through teacher autonomy support. *Zhe He, Beijing Normal University; Ning Ren, The Chinese University of Hong Kong*
- Chair: *Amal Mahmoud Rizk Elassi, Transylvania University*

94.038-4. Leveraging Intersectional Identity to Name and Resist Dominant Narratives in Formal and Informal Education Spaces (Table 4). Division G - Social Context of Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

- Beyond Experiential Education: Focusing on Intersectionality of Youth Learners in Organized Sport. *Levone Lee, University of Kentucky*
- Gender Ideologies and Academic Field Choice: Distinguishing Values and Beliefs in Higher Education Students. *Irina Gewinner, Leibniz University Hanover; Andreas Hadjar, University of Fribourg (Switzerland)*
- Speaking back to power: Lived experiences through counternarratives and counter-masternarratives of race and gender. *Arisandy Johnson, Arizona State University*
- "They're Trying, but They're Doing a Really Crappy Job": Barriers to LGBTQ Inclusion at an Urban High School. *Nina Mauceri, Independent Scholar*
- Enduring Dual Linguistic Terrorism: Critical Language Testimonios of Latina Scholars. *Esmeralda Muñoz,*

University of California - Riverside; Sofia Lisseth Rivas, University of California - Riverside
Chair: *Arisandy Johnson, Arizona State University*

94.038-5. Art, Creativity, Intersectionality And Participatory Approaches To Decolonial Education (Table 5). SIG-Decolonial, Postcolonial, and Anti-Colonial Studies in Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

- A Bedouin Palestinian Expression of Decolonial Solidarity: Reading Laguna Literature in Palestine. *Saeid Alhajahjeh, Al Quds Bard College; Maxine Saeida Sharp, Portland State University*
- Children Art Up: Bilingual Spaces for Collective Decolonial Arts Pedagogical Interventions in Trumpist Times. *Blanca Gabriela Caldas Chumbes, University of Minnesota; Mariane de Araujo Batista-McCulloch, University of Minnesota; Claudia Patricia Mesa-Villa, Universidad de Antioquia*
- El Mundo Zurdo & the Posthuman: A Diffractive Consideration of This Bridge Called My Back. *Nick DePascal, University of New Mexico*
- Using intersectionality: A critical reflection of how coloniality crosses the process of knowledge production. *Francisca Irelva Figueroa-Vidal, Pennsylvania State University; Roxana Chiappa, Universidad de Tarapaca; Maure Aguirre-Ortega, Pennsylvania State University*
- From Servingness to ServingWith: Participatory Action Research to Cultivate Transformative Leadership and Praxis at a dual MSI. *Cynthia D. Villarreal, Northern Arizona University; Lauren R. Contreras, Northern Arizona University; Renee White Eyes, Northern Arizona University; Catharyn Crane Shelton, Northern Arizona University; Darold H. Joseph, Northern Arizona University; Alma Montemayor Sandigo, Northern Arizona University - Yuma; Gerald K. Wood, Northern Arizona University; Christine Keller Lemley, Northern Arizona University*
- Chair: *Adnan Turan, Arizona State University*

94.038-6. Eisner and Contemporary Research (Table 6). SIG-Elliot Eisner; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

- Cultivating Experience Through Lesson Sketching. *Daniel R. Conn, Minot State University; Christy McConnell, University of Northern Colorado*
- Being an Arts-based Researcher: An Autoethnographic Examination of an Unconventional Academic Career Path. *Robert B. Donmoyer, University of San Diego*
- Using Educational Criticism to Gain Insight into Teacher's Understanding of, Perceptions about, and Attitudes Towards

Divisive Concepts Legislation. *Todd M Hodgkinson, Drake University; Caroline Jernigan Conner, Kennesaw State University; Aubrey Brammar Southall, Aurora University; Crystal Howell, Randolph College*

Teaching Toward Plurality: Black, Queer, and White Women Educators Reimagining Teacher Education. *Michelle Zoss, Georgia State University; Marie Ojofeitimi, Georgia State University; Joshua Daniel McCall, Atlanta Public Schools*

Chair: *Edith P. Middleton, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Discussants: *Sheila R. Vaidya, Drexel University; Ida Oberman, Alanus University of Arts and Social Sciences; Patience Amadu, University of Colorado - Colorado Springs*

94.038-7. Youth, Place, and Environmental Citizenship (Table 7). SIG-Environmental Education; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Constitutional Commitments, Civic Consequences: Whether Environmental Provisions Shape Youth Eco-Citizenship Across 22 Countries. *Darren Rabinowitz, Teachers College, Columbia University*

Environmental Education through School Clubs: Impact on the Ecological Knowledge and Attitudes of Primary School Students in Morocco – case of the province of Marrakech-. *Jabrane Amaghous, Cadi Ayyad University*

Understanding What Shapes Environmental Awareness in Hong Kong Grade 8 Students: Evidence from TIMSS 2023. *Lifen Hu, University at Albany - SUNY*

The Benefits and Pitfalls of an Urban Foraging-Based Environmental Education Program. *Dafna Gan, The Open University of Israel*

Student activism to save a university farm: toward a grounded theory of community-valued places. *Sarah Stapleton, University of Oregon*

Discussant: *Amelia Lynn King-Kostelac, University of Texas - San Antonio*

94.038-8. Access and Success in Higher Education: Advising, Belonging, and Participation (Table 8). SIG-Asian Americans and Pacific Islanders in Education and Research; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Does Culturally Responsive Advising Matter? A Quantitative Analysis of the Relationships of Advising to Social Outcomes. *Emily Petruzzelli Schell, University of Colorado - Boulder*

Exploring the Factors that Inform Pacific Island AANAPISI's Approach to Serving AA&NHPI Students. *Demeturie Toso-Lafaele Gogue, University of Massachusetts - Boston; Kristine Jan Cruz Espinoza, California Lutheran University; Odorico San Nicolas, University of California, Los Angeles;*

Kaelani Babauta Demapan, Northern Marianas College; Mike Hoa Nguyen, University of California - Los Angeles
Unapologetically Belong: Fostering Critical Consciousness of AAPI Community College Students through Capstone Projects. *Katlin Choi, San Diego Mesa College*

Why Disaggregation Matters: Understanding Achievement Gaps Among Asian American Students. *Xinyi Mao, University of Central Florida; Se Woong Lee, University of Missouri; Jia Liang, Kansas State University*

Chair: *Lei Jiang, University of Kansas*

94.038-9. AsianCrit in Action: Theory, Method, and Transformative Curriculum (Table 9). SIG-Asian Americans and Pacific Islanders in Education and Research; Roundtable Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Petree D; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Asian Graduate Students' Experiences: Utilizing AsianCrit both as Theory and Methodology. *Robert J. Lynn, Texas Tech University; Ryuto Hashimoto, University of Missouri*
“Not Just Numbers”: Reimagining Financial Literacy Curriculum Through AsianCrit. *Jin A Jung, University of Toronto - OISE*

What Do We Know about AsianCrit in Education Research?: A Systematic Review. *Yiting Chu, University of South Florida - Tampa*

Chair: *Shuzhan Li, Ithaca College*

94.039. AERA Roundtable Session Sunday 1:45 pm;
Roundtable Session

94.039-1. Roundtable Session 10: Student Learning and Development in College and Beyond (Table 1). Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Effect of Parenting Styles on the Social Emotional Wellbeing of Tertiary Students. *Ruth Keziah Annan-Brew, University of Cape Coast; Eric Anane, University of Cape Coast; Ebenezer Takyi-Wadieh, Ohio University; Enoch Tsey, University of Cape Coast; Cletus Owusu Yeboah, Ohio University*

“Learning to Learn Better”: Metacognitive Self-Appraisal and Self-Management among Undergraduate Students. *Ralitsa Todorova, University of Southern California*

Rethinking Reading in Writing Centers: A Content Analysis for Imagining Future Literacies. *Nasim Layegh, Texas State University; Emily Suh, Texas State University; Lance S. Womack, Texas State University; Ali Dezhkameh Bejoshin, Texas State University; Elahe Mahmoudi, Texas State University*

Transfronterix Identity Development: A Photovoice Grounded

Theory Model of College Students at the Borderlands.
Vannessa Falcón Orta, San Diego State University

94.039-2. Career and Post-Graduation Plans (Table 2).

Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Importance of Relational Closeness in Career Development for Students from Low-income Backgrounds. *Ronald Hallett, University of Southern California; Joseph Kitchen, University of Southern California*

Examining Differences between Early Exiters and Program Completers for the Inclusive Career Advancement Program. *Jennifer Brooks, Cornell University; Valerie Malzer, Cornell University; Katherine Brendli Brown, Cornell University; Leslie Shaw, Cornell University*

The Urban-rural Gap of Chinese College Graduates's Employment Outcomes. *Qinxue Feng, Nanjing University; Changjun Yue, Peking University; Yuting Guan, Peking University*

Chair: *Elaine Jessica Castillo Tamargo, California State University - Long Beach*

94.039-3. Predictors of institutional Sustainability: enrollment and other considerations (Table 3).

Division J - Postsecondary Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Colleges in Competition? Effects of Tuition-Free Policies on Two- and Four-Year College Funding and Enrollment. *Daniel Sparks, University of Arkansas*

Shuttered Halls: Synthesizing the Silent Collapse of American Higher Education. *Jaden Alexandra Mikoulinskii, University of Georgia; Jordan Mackenzie Mitchell, University of Georgia; Abigail Affholter, University of Georgia*

Winners and Losers of the National Enrollment Decline: Institutional Characteristics Driving First-Time-in-College Enrollment Trends. *Dong Chen, University of Arizona; Anwasha Guha, University of Oregon; Kurt Williams, North Dakota State University; Amleset Abrhale, Howard University*

94.039-4. Beliefs, Practices, and Identities: Reframing Mathematics Teaching Through a Human-Centered Lens (Table 4).

Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Content-Specific Noticing Among Early-Career Mathematics Teachers. *Yasemin Copur-Gencturk, University of Southern California; Ahreum Han, University of Southern California*

Profiles of Preservice Teachers' Mathematics Beliefs: A Person-Centered Analysis of Anxiety and Instructional Orientation. *Jessie Store, Saginaw Valley State University*
Reframing Mathematics Anxiety: A Critical Literature Review of Instructional Practices in K-8 Classrooms. *Peter Damilare Idowu, Florida State University; Kolawole Kushimo, University of Massachusetts - Dartmouth; Olayinka Joshua Oyewole, Florida State University; Ohwatosin Deborah Akande, King's college Lagos, Nigeria*

Written Feedback as a Window into Teachers' Mindset Beliefs in Elementary Mathematics. *Kyle A. Moreno, University of Southern California; Yasemin Copur-Gencturk, University of Southern California; Danielle Silvaggio, University of San Diego*

Understanding and Supporting High School Mathematics Teachers' Culturally Responsive Mathematics Assessment and Teaching. *Lawrence Teng, University of Texas at Austin; Yasmyn Irizarry, University of Texas at Austin; Tia C. Madkins, The University of Texas at Austin*

Chair: *Yasemin Copur-Gencturk, University of Southern California*

Discussant: *Nathan Alexander, Howard University*

94.039-5. Against the Tide: Teachers of Color Navigating Challenging School Contexts (Table 5).

Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Black Educator Voices Matter: Perceptions, Preparation, and Support for Culturally Relevant and Sustaining Pedagogical Practices. *Katina L Thomas, Prairie View A&M University*

Creating Kinetic Counterspaces for Wellness: Teacher Educators of Color In it for the Long Run. *Diane Nevarez, California State University - Stanislaus; Arturo Nevarez, California State University - Stanislaus; Daniel Soodjinda, California State University - Stanislaus*

Forced to Code-Switch: The Protection and Resistance of Latinx Educators Amidst Relentless Pressures to Assimilate. *Paula Sevilla, University of California - Santa Barbara*

Troubling Racial Climates in Teacher Education and Imagining Equitable Futures for Aspiring Teachers of Color. *John Pascarella, University of Southern California; Jihye Kwon, University of Southern California*

Chair: *Sophie Rebecca Korn Gallagher, Los Angeles County Office of Education*

Discussant: *Sophie Rebecca Korn Gallagher, Los Angeles County Office of Education*

94.039-6. Curriculum as Policy, Curriculum as Power: Whose Knowledge Counts? (Table 6).

Division L - Educational Policies and Politics; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

High School Effects on Civic Engagement. *Kirsten Slungaard Mumma, Teachers College, Columbia University*

How Did We Get Here and What's Next? A Landscape Analysis of Civics Education. *Amanda R. Baker, The George Washington University; Katie Kinnaman, The George Washington University; Paul Goren, Northwestern University*

Implementing the TEAACH Act: Asian American Teachers' Perceptions, Barriers, and Supports. *Hyeungok Kang, California State University - San Bernardino; Su Yon Choi, Michigan State University; Jonga Lee, Sungkyunkwan University; Jeong Yeon Park, California State University - Fullerton*

Why Is Youth Civic Engagement So Low? Civics Amnesia and Other Educational Barriers. *Ashley J. Carey, Sacred Heart University; Lance Piantaggini, University of Massachusetts - Amherst; Salma Baksh, Smith College; Jack Schneider, University of Massachusetts - Amherst*

Chair: *Ashley J. Carey, Sacred Heart University*

94.039-7. AI, Technology, Digital Literacy, and Computational Thinking in Early Childhood (Table 7). SIG-Early Education and Child Development; Roundtable Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Integrating Bits and Beats: A Scoping Review of Computational Thinking and Music in Early Learning. *Elaine Lam, The Education University of Hong Kong; Weipeng Yang, The Education University of Hong Kong*

An AI-Powered Project Approach to Fostering Children's Computational Thinking: A Quasi-Experimental Study. *Weipeng Yang, The Education University of Hong Kong; Sixuan Xiang, The Education University of Hong Kong*

Artificial Intelligence in Early Years Education: A Scoping Review of Technologies, Users, and Developmental Outcomes. *Esther Yu, University of Toronto - OISE; Samantha Burns, University of Guelph; Joel Wiebe, University of Toronto - OISE; Michal Perlman, University of Toronto - OISE*

From Flipping Pages to Scrolling Screens: Exploring Emergent Digital Literacy Behaviors of Young Children. *Amanda M. Mirabella, University of North Carolina Asheville; Ilene R. Berson, University of South Florida; Jolyn Blank, University of South Florida; Michael J. Berson, University of South Florida; Lisa M. Lopez, University of South Florida*

Artificial Intelligence With and for Children: Scoping Review. *Shinho Kim, Framingham State University; Kyung Hwa Lee, University of Georgia; Gyu Lim Choi, University of Georgia; Katherine C. Cheng, University of Arizona; Naeun Yun, University of Georgia; Sung Eun Jung, University of Arizona; Hyeungok Kang, California State University - San Bernardino; Soo Won Shim, Illinois State University;*

Xiaoying Zhao, Illinois State University

Chair: *Amanda M. Mirabella, University of North Carolina Asheville*

94.039-8. Executive Function and Social-Emotional Development in Early Childhood (Table 8). SIG-Early Education and Child Development; Roundtable Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

From COVID to 2025: Modeling Enduring Chain of Hardship, Parental Distress and Child Emotional Distress. *WooJung Kim, Stanford University; Phil Fisher, Stanford University*

Depression in Caregivers of Young Children Ages 0-5 Years Old. *Hongxia Zhao, University of North Alabama; Qiuju Tian, Kean University*

Are Associations between Classroom Quality and Children's Social-Emotional Development Moderated by Child Marginalization? *Zhiling Meng Shea, University of Nevada, Las Vegas; Jiacan He, University of California - Santa Cruz; Siyuan Chen, College of William & Mary*

Examining the Longitudinal Impact of an Executive Function-Focused Program on Pre-Kindergarten and Kindergarten Student Achievement. *Amber L. Brown, University of Houston - Clear Lake; Michelle L. Peters, University of Houston - Clear Lake; Susan Jackson, Goose Creek CISD*

Exploring patterns of children's executive function and their association with social-emotional competence: a latent profile analysis. *Mengyan Fang, Shaanxi Normal University; Chenyi Zhang, Georgia State University*

Chair: *Amber L. Brown, University of Houston - Clear Lake*

94.039-9. Staying Power: Narrating Teacher Identity and Becoming (Table 9). SIG-Narrative Research; Roundtable Session JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 1; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Why Is It So Hard to Say Goodbye? Exploring Teacher Retention and Thriving Through Narrative Inquiry. *DaJuana Chaney Fontenot, Texas A&M University*

Mentoring: The backbone of an interwoven teacher education and teaching community. *Paige K. Evans, University of Houston; Donna Stokes, University of Houston; Cheryl J. Craig, Texas A&M University; Gayle A. Curtis, Texas A&M University; Karla Adelina Garza, University of Houston; Karen E. McIntush, University of Houston*

"You Know How to Deal with These Problems with Your Students, Not as a Teacher": Learning to Teach as Racialized Experiences. *William J. Davis, Southern Utah University*

Narrative Accompaniment: Taking Up Professional Development as an Ethical and Relational Practice. *Ginger Barnhart, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill*

Chair: *Gayle A. Curtis, Texas A&M University*

94.040. AERA Roundtable Session Sunday 1:45 pm - Gold 2;
Roundtable Session

**94.040-1. Teacher Experiences in the Mathematics Classroom:
From Intentions to Interpretations (Table 1).** SIG-
Research in Mathematics Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Algebra 1 Teachers' Experiences in an RPP-Based PLC
Implementing a New Mathematics Curriculum. *Mitchelle M
Wambua, Washington University in St. Louis*

From Mistake-Making to Sense-Making in the Classroom: How
Teacher Intentions Construct Revision in Mathematics
Environments. *Hannah Carlan, Washington State
University; Heather Byington, Washington State University;
Raisa June Ebner, Washington State University - Tri-Cities;
Jonah B. Firestone, Washington State University - Tri-
Cities; Ethan P. Smith, Washington State University - Tri-
Cities*

From Perception to Appreciation: How Teachers Interpret
Student Work in Problem-Based Mathematics Lessons.
*Qiuyu Chen, University of Michigan; Patricio G. Herbst,
University of Michigan*

Mathematics Teachers' Sensemaking of Teaching Multilingual
Students. *Devan MacKenzie, North Carolina State
University; Samantha Marshall, North Carolina State
University; Sunghwan Byun, North Carolina State
University; Kerianne Peadar, North Carolina State
University*

Sparkling the Flame: Cultivating Joy in Mathematics for
Preservice and Early Career Teachers. *Gregory Benoit,
Boston University; Aaron Brakoniecki, Boston University;
Eric Cordero-Siy, Boston University*

Chair: *Lisa Amick, University of Kentucky*

**94.040-2. Traversing Global Perspectives of the Mathematics
Classroom (Table 2).** SIG-Research in Mathematics
Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Flexibility in the Making: Comparing Multiple Strategies in
Chinese Algebra Classrooms. *Haoyi Wang, University of
Toronto; Qiuyu Chen, University of Michigan; Rui Chen,
Columbia University; Jon R. Star, Harvard University*

Global Insights into Early Algebra: A Cross-Country Analysis
of Elementary Curricula. *Iwan Andi Jonri Sianturi, SUNY -
College at Oswego; Manto Lumban Gaol, State University of
Medan*

How Math Homework Types Influence Student Academic
Performance? A Chain Mediation Analysis in the Chinese

Context. *Mucheng Zhang, Beijing Normal University;
Yueyang Shao, Beijing Normal University; Jian Liu, Beijing
Normal University*

Understanding Values, Practices, and their Alignment
Regarding Incorporating Histories into Mathematics
Classrooms. *Praveen Chhikara; Rochelle Gutierrez,
University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Unpacking the Language of Math: Semiotic and Contextual
Demands in Ontario's Standardized Math Assessment.
Rosalia Cha, University of Toronto - OISE

Chair: *Sandra Zuniga, San José State University*

94.040-3. Literacies and language development (Table 3). SIG-
Bilingual Education Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Helpful or Hindering? Pop-Up Dictionary Effects on Bilingual
Children's Reading Comprehension. *Krystina Raymond, San
Diego State University; Samantha Burns, University of
Guelph*

High School English Learner Language Development: Impact
of SEL-Embedded SIOP Model on ESL Teacher Practice.
*Rui Niu-Cooper, Grand Valley State University; Jeffrey D.
Greene, Western Michigan University*

Language, Trauma, and Teacher Well-Being: Exploring
Trauma-Informed Practices Oracy-Biliteracy Instruction in
Rural Multilingual Classrooms. *Santiago Parra Giraldo,
Purdue University; Ofelia Castro Schepers, Purdue
University*

Reviewing a quarter century of bilingual speech language
pathology: Imagining new futures with bilingual education.
*Joseph Hin Yan Lam, University of California - Irvine;
Cecilia Perez, University of Southern California; Melissa
Mendoza, Texas Christian University; Steve Daniel Przymus,
University of Rhode Island; Audrey M. Sorrells, Texas
Christian University*

Translanguaging in the Bilingual Writing Centre to Facilitate
Literacy Development of Chinese International
Undergraduates. *Cong Wang, University of Illinois at
Urbana-Champaign*

**94.040-4. Narrating Language Resistance and Agency (Table
4).** SIG-Bilingual Education Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Negotiating Identity: Multiracial Students in Mandarin-English
Bilingual Classrooms. *Jasmine Pham, University of Toronto
- OISE*

Nuestro Español Mocho Tiene Valor: Paradoxical Messaging in
Multilingualism. *Silvia Tovar, University of California -
Davis; Claudia Rodriguez-Mojica, University of California -
Davis; Allison Briceno, San José State University; Sara*

Rutherford-Quach, SRI Education

Resistance as Investment in Heritage Language Learning: Reimagining Investment by Centering Community Cultural Wealth. *Jung-In Kim, University of Colorado - Denver*
Rest as Resistance: Transcendental Meditation, Cultural Wealth, and the Well-Being of Bilingual Teacher-Leaders. *Margaret Peterson, Stanford University*
We Are All Translanguaging People: Identity and Social Dynamics Among Chinese Transnational Doctoral Students. *Shuai Xu, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

94.040-5. Places and Possibilities for Equity, Justice, and Belonging (Table 5). SIG-Critical Educators for Social Justice; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Engineering Belonging: How a Robotics Program Fostered STEM Identity Through Social Influence. *Shikhar Kashyap, Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University; Brenda R. Brand, Virginia Tech; Lezly Taylor, Virginia Tech*
Tribal self-determination or political status quo: From blueprint to home-school and community collaborations. *Mere Berryman, University of Waikato; Elizabeth Martha Ann Eley, University of Waikato; Suzanne SooHoo, Chapman University*
Pláticas and Femtorship as Pathways for Advocacy, Mentorship, and Healing in Education. *Margarita Jimenez-Silva, University of California - Davis; Janine Bempechat, Boston University; Eleonora Villegas-Reimers, Boston University; Patricia D. Quijada Cerecer, University of California - Davis; Melody Esqueda, Northeastern University; Evelyn C. Baca, Illinois State University; Leticia Alvarez Gutiérrez, University of Utah*
Chair: *Richard V. Kahn, Antioch University*

94.040-6. Racial Justice Fatigue: Reckoning with Whiteness and Transformation in Teacher Education (Table 6). SIG-Critical Educators for Social Justice; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

More than the Minimum: Culturally Responsive Evaluation in the Pursuit of Racial Justice at Hispanic-Serving Institutions. *Rick Sperling, St. Mary's University (TX); Daniel Cheshire, Our Lady of the Lake University*
Negotiating Anti-Racist Teacher Identities in Post-Pandemic Urban Classrooms. *Marinda K. Harrell-Levy, Pennsylvania State University - Brandywine*
Teacher Educators of Color as Collateral Damage: The Harm of Performative “Racial Justice” in Teacher Education. *Rita Kohli, University of California - Riverside; Marcos Pizarro, California State University - Los Angeles; Emily Dech,*

University of California - Riverside

The Limits of Antiracism: Abolition as a Transformative Alternative. *Abby C. Emerson, Touro University*
Whiteness as a Barrier to Advancing Critical Teaching Practices for Teachers of Color. *Kim Vachon, University of California - Santa Cruz*
Chair: *Tiffani J. Smith, LA Mission College*

94.040-7. Building Capacity in Career and Technical Education and Workplace Learning (Table 7). SIG-Career & Technical Education and Workplace Learning; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Advancing the Semiconductor Workforce: Shifts in Engagement and Influence Across Institutions in a Regional Consortium. *Silvia Jessica Mostacedo Marasovic, University of Texas - Arlington; Katherine street hoover, University of Texas at Arlington; Jin Liu, University of Texas - Arlington; Sindhura Suravarjula, University of Texas - Arlington; Cory T. Forbes, University of Texas - Arlington*
Bridging the Research Gap: Developing Research Capacity in Graduate Career and Technical Education Programs. *Katherine R. Kandalec Holm, Athens State University; Michelle E. Bartlett, Old Dominion University*
The Role of Institution Type in Postsecondary Enrollment for High School Students. *Brett D. Campbell, Utah System of Higher Education*
Using Quantitative Ethnography to Explore Interdisciplinary Collaboration in a CTE Building and Construction Pathway. *Jonathan L. Montoya, Saint Mary's College (CA); Ryan Lundell, Santa Clara University; Anthony M. Perry, University of North Dakota; Brendan R. Eagan, University of Wisconsin - Madison*
Running a Business in High School: Student Selection into Virtual Enterprises. *Tiffany Berglund, RAND Corporation; Lindsay Daugherty, RAND Corporation; Katherine Hughes, EdWordian, LLC; Umut Ozek, RAND Corporation; Nazia Wolters, RAND Corporation*
Chair: *Jay Plasman, The Ohio State University*
Discussant: *Adam K. Atwell, Old Dominion University*

94.040-8. Critical Examination of Race, Ethnicity, Class, and Gender Roundtable: Supporting Students' Racial Identity Development and Academic Success (Table 8). SIG-Critical Examination of Race, Ethnicity, Class and Gender in Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Centering Men of Color in Higher Education: Constructing Cultural Wealth, Sense of Belonging, and Vulnerability. *Leon P. Strayer, California State Polytechnic University -*

Pomona; Reggie Robles, Claremont Graduate University
“Came off more like wardens than teachers:” Black students’
retrospective reflections on effective teaching and
mentorship. *Marcia J. Watson-Vandiver, Towson University;*
Deneen S. Dixon-Payne, Towson University
Institutional Ethnography: Illuminating Intersectional
(In)Equities in Advisement at a Southwestern Minority
Serving Institution (SMSI). *Lacey Shanté Hites, University*
of New Mexico

Chair: *Khalilah Odessa Ali, Spelman College*

**94.040-9. Teacher Learning, Collaboration, and Efficacy for
Educational Change (Table 9).** SIG-Educational Change;
Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 2;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Can We Rely on Collaboration? Exploring Protective Factors
Against Teacher Burnout and Self-Efficacy Loss. *Joonkil*
Ahn, University of Arizona; Seora Park, University of
Arizona

Cross-Sector Collaboration in Hawai‘i’s Early Childhood
Mixed-Delivery System. *Manca Sustarsic, University of*
Hawai‘i at Manoa; Nicole Schlaack, University of Hawai‘i
at Manoa

Differentiated Gains: How Experience Moderates the Impact of
Professional Learning Communities. *Eunji Koh, The Ohio*
State University

K-5 Teachers' Knowledge and Understanding of Trauma
Informed Education Impacts Their Students Academically
and Behaviorally. *Dana Mikell McGinnis, Lake Elsinore*
Unified School District

Chair: *Joonkil Ahn, University of Arizona*

94.041. AERA Roundtable Session Sunday 1:45 pm - Gold 3;
Roundtable Session

**94.041-1. Methodology, Measurement, and Mechanisms to
Social Emotional Learning (Table 1).** SIG-Social and
Emotional Learning; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Differential Associations Between Facets of Mindfulness and
Forgiveness: The Roles of Nonjudgment and Awareness.
Zachary T. Schornick, University of Alabama; Kristina L.
McDonald, University of Alabama; Summer Braun,
University of Alabama

Secondary School Students’ Social and Emotional Skills and
Academic Literacy: A Latent Profile Analysis. *Hong Zhang,*
East China Normal University; Mengnan Zhang; Qianyu
Zhou, East China Normal University; Niu Ruan, East China
Normal University; Lixin Wang, Chongqing University

Self-Centered Civic Engagement? A Systematic Literature

Review of Social-Emotional Learning in Civics Education
Research. *Tom Nachtigal, Stanford University; Ariana*
Zetlin, University of Pennsylvania

The Development and Validation of a New 7-Dimensional SEL
Scale. *I-Hsuan Chen, National Cheng Kung University; Hsu-*
Chan Kuo, National Cheng Kung University

Chair: *Almut K. Zieher, Yale University*

**94.041-2. Critical Approaches to Artificial Intelligence and
Literacies (Table 2).** SIG-Writing and Literacies;

Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Advanced Multilingual Writers’ Self-Directed Use of
Generative AI in Academic Writing: Rethinking Writing,
Authorship, and Learning. *Chaoran Wang, Colby College;*
Wei Xu, Northern Illinois University; Xiao Tan, Utah State
University

“A Bit Unease With This Policy”: How Preservice Teachers
Construct Classroom Policies for Generative AI in ELA
Classrooms. *Brady L. Nash, University of Florida; Sarah*
Burriss, Vanderbilt University

Problematising Equity Issues in Multiliteracies and Use of
Generative AI: Why Critical Ethical Literacy Matters. *Nari*
Kim, Michigan State University; Vashti Wai Yu Lee,
Brigham Young University; Sonja Mecham, Michigan State
University; Peter I. De Costa, Michigan State University

Writing ‘Right’: Teacher praxis in the age of artificial
intelligence. *Victoria Henry, Teachers College, Columbia*
University; Dorsa Ivana Fahami, Teachers College,
Columbia University; Adrienne Vitullo, Teachers College

Chair: *Zixin Chen, University of Washington*

**94.041-3. Becoming Scientists: Pathways of Identity, Interest,
and Belonging (Table 3).** Division C - Learning and
Instruction; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

“Choosing What’s Important to Me!”: Impacts of the Co-
Design Process on Fifth-Grade Girl’s Science Interests.
Jasmyne Yeldell, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill
Khalid, University of Arizona; Priscila M Ledezma,
University of Arizona; Kealie Walker, University of Arizona;
Adriana D. Cimetta, University of Arizona; Courtney
Leligdon, University of Arizona; Kimberly Sierra, University
of Arizona

Gendered pathways in science: A fuzzy-set analysis of high
science-achieving students’ career expectations. *Shaohui*
Chi, East China Normal University; Zuhao Wang, East
China Normal University

How Inquiry-Based Learning Impacts Science Career

Expectations: Mediating Roles of Achievement Motivation and Science Identity. *Jiayi Tao, East China Normal University; Shaohui Chi, East China Normal University; Zuhao Wang, East China Normal University; Wenye Zhou, Institute of Curriculum and Instruction East China Normal University*

The Impact of an NIH-Funded Project on Students' STEM Self-Efficacy, Science Identity, and Career Interest. *Sunha Kim, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Weiyi Ding, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Stephen Koury, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Sandra Small, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

94.041-4. Meta-analytic and Systematic Reviews of Learning Environments (Table 4). Division C - Learning and Instruction; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

An Initial Systematic Literature Review: STEM Identity Development in Formal High School Settings. *Thomas Daniel Armour, University of Miami; Jennifer Beth Kahn, University of Miami*

Detangling the Connection Between Teacher Support and Student Engagement in Math Education: A Meta-Analytic Perspective. *Qi Zhang, American Institutes for Research; Li Yibing, American Institutes for Research; Ming-Te Wang, University of Chicago*

Does Artificial Intelligence-Powered Educational Agents Affect Students' Learning? Evidence From a Meta-Analysis. *Shuai LIU, East China Normal University; Hao Lei, East China Normal University; Zhuotao Lu, Qingdao University; Xin Liu, East China Normal University*

Reimagining Informal STEM Learning Ecosystems: A Systematic Review of Outcomes for Underrepresented and Underserved Learners. *Saki L. Milton, Southern Methodist University*

SFL and ESP Writing Instruction: A Systematic Review of Pedagogical Approaches. *Lutfi Ashar Mauludin, The Ohio State University; Triubaida Maya Ardianti, The Ohio State University*

Chair: *Krisanna L. Machtmes, Ohio University*

94.041-5. AI in Student Learning: Programming, Writing, and Engagement (Table 5). Division C - Learning and Instruction; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

A Generative AI-assisted Intervention to Promote High School Students' Personal Relevance to Math and Interest in the Math Class. *Zhixing Guo; Luke Fryer, University of Hong Kong; Alex Shum, University of Hong Kong*

Co-designing with teachers an online education program for youth to navigate AI-mediated cyber risks. *Wenting Zou,*

Pennsylvania State University; Huanying Song, Pennsylvania State University; Yu-Jou Joyce Chou, Pennsylvania State University; Jiaju Lin, Pennsylvania State University; Feiwen Xiao, University of Pennsylvania

Examining Undergraduate Students' Thinking Processes and Programming Performance When Using Web Search and Generative AI. *Tianlong Zhong, Nanyang Technological University; Gaoxia Zhu, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University*

Human-AI Collaborative Learning and Critical Thinking Development: Evidence from a Technology-Enriched Graduate Course. *Yinuo Li, university of bristol*

Self-Efficacy and Strategy in AI-Assisted Academic Writing: A Longitudinal Study of Chinese EFL Doctoral Students. *Huanqing Li, Tsinghua University; Qian Guo, Tsinghua University; Yanyu Wang, Tsinghua University*

Chair: *Yetunde Omoyiwole Fawehinmi, Texas A&M University*

94.041-6. RT1: Measurement and Related Issues in Quantitative Research Designs, Analysis, and Simulation (Table 6). Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

How Well Does Monte Carlo Simulation Perform in Generating Datasets Under the IRT 3PL Model? *Ergul Demir, Ankara University*

Cognitive Engagement Measurement in Online Learning Using Eye-Tracking Data and Back Propagation Neural Networks. *jialin zhou, East China Normal University; Zhan Chen, East China Normal University; Yaofeng Xue, East China Normal University; 扣琪王, East China Normal University; yiwei gou, East China Normal University*

Bayesian Estimation of MIMIC Models Under Small-Sample Conditions and Latent Outlier Contamination. *Nancy Alila, University of Georgia*

Testing for Item Level Disparities Using Zero-Inflation Models in NAFS. *Fathima Mohrrag Jaffari, National Center for Assessment; Georgios D. Sideridis, Harvard University*

Possible Solutions to Heywood Cases in Confirmatory Factor Analysis. *Yijun Cheng, University of Washington; Weicong Lyu, University of Macau; Oscar L. Olvera Astivia, University of Washington*

94.041-7. Access as Method: Adaptive, Embodied, and Disability-Centered Approaches to Qualitative Inquiry (Table 7). Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Gold Level, Gold 3;
1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

From Lived Experience to Theory: Developing the Equity and Justice Framework for Inclusive Teaching. *Kristen*

Smigielski, University at Buffalo - SUNY / CELaRAI
Neurodiverse Spacetime: Methodological Examples.
Corey Reutlinger, Arizona State University; Mirka E. Koro, Arizona State University; Seth Thorn, Arizona State University; Margarita Pivovarova, Arizona State University; Anani M. Vasquez, Neurodiversity Education Research Center; Olivia Heneddo, Arizona State University
Qualitative Inquiry with Participants with Intellectual Disabilities: Methodological Transformation through Accessibility-Adaptability as Risk. *Andres A. Arrazola, Florida International University*

Chair: *Kristen Smigielski, University at Buffalo - SUNY / CELaRAI*

94.042. AERA Roundtable Session Sunday 1:45 pm - Gold 4;
Roundtable Session

94.042-1. Applying Mixed Methods for Understanding Experience, Action, and Organizational Change in Higher Education (Table 1). Division D - Measurement and Research Methodologies Cosponsored with SIG-Mixed Methods Research; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

A Mixed Methods Approach to Mapping Understanding to Experience. *Sebnem Cilesiz, University of Louisiana at Lafayette; Emily K. Sandoz, University of Louisiana at Lafayette; Anna Catherine Romero, University of Southern Mississippi*

Learning from Mixed Methods Participatory Action Research with Latine Young Adults: Insights for Educational Researchers. *Kevin Ferreira van Leer, University of Connecticut; Amber Michelle Gonzalez, California State University - Sacramento*

Perceived Organizational Support After DEI Removal: A Mixed Methods Study of Undergraduate Experiences. *Ariannely Hernandez, University of Alabama; Eric Hernandez, University of Alabama*

Chair: *Marcia Gail Headley, University of Delaware*

94.042-2. Advancing Reading and Math Achievement in Elementary Schools (Table 2). Division H - Research, Evaluation and Assessment in Schools; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Accelerating Third Grade Reading Achievement in a Rural, Multilingual District: A Multi-Measure, Systemic Literacy Reform. *Adrienne Minnerly, Shelton School District; Wyeth Jessee, Shelton School District*

Examining Targeted Skills Instruction Program Effects on English Language Arts Achievements: A Regression Discontinuity Approach. *Weiling Li, Edmentum; Emma Somer, Edmentum; Amy J. Dray, Edmentum*

School-Level Math RTI Implementation and Elementary Math Growth: A Multilevel Propensity-Weighted Analysis of the ECLS-K:2011. *Qi Wang, Florida State University; Garret Hall, Florida State University; Qian Zhang, Florida State University*

Unpacking Inequality in Kindergarten Math Achievement: Cognitive and Contextual Predictors Using Random Coefficients Modelling. *Abiodun Emmanuel Babalola, University of Alabama; Alison Hooper, University of Alabama; Joon-Ho Lee, University of Alabama*

Discussant: *Yuliya Ardasheva, Washington State University - Tri Cities*

94.042-3. Feedback as a Catalyst for Learning: Faculty Practices, Student Engagement, and Assessment Innovation (Table 3). SIG-Measurement and Assessment in Higher Education; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Assessment Futures: Student Voices on Fairness, Feedback, and Evaluation Reform. *Sema Sulak, Bartin University*

From External Feedback to Internal Responsibility: Examining the Interplay between Feedback Social Awareness and Accountability. *Lijie Qin, The Education University of Hong Kong; Lan Yang, Education University of Hong Kong*

From Receiving to Seeking: Validating a Five-Factor Feedback Orientation Scale in Japanese Higher Education. *Lan Yang, Education University of Hong Kong; Mayu Koike Ban, Institute of Science Tokyo; Midori Ban, Osaka University*
How Classroom Culture Regulates Students' Perceptions of Self-Generated Feedback in University Mathematics: A Disciplinary Perspective. *Min Deng, The University of Hong Kong*

Mapping Student Feedback Literacy: A Scoping Review of Qualitative Evidence in Higher Education. *Lijie Qin, The Education University of Hong Kong; Lan Yang, Education University of Hong Kong*

Chair: *Marissa Green-Francescon, University of Iowa*
Discussant: *Serafina Pastore, University of Bari*

94.042-4. Igniting Motivation: Complementary Perspectives on Motivating Climates and Socializers (Table 4). SIG-Motivation in Education Cosponsored with Division C - Learning and Instruction; Roundtable Session
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Instructional Quality and Academic Help-Seeking: Do CLASS Codes Predict Growth? *Amos Jeng, University of Michigan; Kai S. Cortina, University of Michigan*

Students' Perceptions of Socializers' Mindsets and Their Influences: A Qualitative Thematic Analysis. *Wonjoon Cha, The Ohio State University; Sungwha Kim, Korea University*

- *Brain and Motivation Research Institute; Hyun Ji Lee, Hunter College, The City University of New York; Eric M. Anderman, The Ohio State University*

Triggering and Developing Students' Interest in Reading. A Systematic Review of Instructional Practices. *Bente Rigmor Walgermo, University of Stavanger; Erin McTigue, University of Stavanger; K. Ann Renninger, Swarthmore College; Per Henning Uppstad, University of Stavanger*

Understanding Competence Beliefs Through Daily Science Instruction: A Mixed-Methods Multiple Case Study. *Stephanie Hyewon Shin, University of Cincinnati (College of Education); Jennifer A. Schmidt, Michigan State University; Lisa Linnenbrink-Garcia, Michigan State University*

Chair: *Adriana I. Martinez Calvit, University of Missouri - St. Louis*

94.042-5. Student Experiences in Online Learning

Environments (Table 5). SIG-Online Teaching and Learning; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Designing a Group Awareness Tool for Online Graduate Non-Traditional Students: A Design-Based Research. *Feliza Marie Mercado, Texas Tech University; Sungwon Shin, Texas Tech University; Min Huang, Texas Tech University*

Exploring Learner Perceptions of Online Assessments. *Stella Yun Kim, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Doris U. Bolliger, Texas Tech University; Florence Martin, North Carolina State University*

From Rigidity to Responsiveness: Post-Pandemic Syllabus Policy Shifts and Student Perceptions of Instruction. *Melissa S. Rame, University of South Florida*

Higher Education Students' Perceptions of Data Privacy in Learning Management Systems. *Hannah Wilhoit, University of North Texas; Deborah Cockerham, University of North Texas*

"I can be whoever I want to be": Using photovoice to understand online student experiences. *Margaretta Underhill, Oregon State University; Mary Ellen Dello Stritto, Oregon State University*

Chair: *Kathleen Scott, Pepperdine University*

94.042-6. Developing PBL futures (Table 6). SIG-Problem-

Based and Project-Based Learning; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Building Future Minds of the 21st Century: Using LEGO® Serious Play® to Foster Entrepreneurship, Positive Psychology, and Financial Literacy at Schools. *Ianina Scheuch, TU Dresden; Baerbel Fuerstenau, Dresden University of Technology*

Integrating AI into Problem-Based Learning to Enhance Pre-

Service Teachers' TPACK and Disposition Toward Mathematics Teaching. *Shuhua An, California State University - Long Beach; Zhonghe Wu, National University; Anahi Javier, California State University - Long Beach*

The Role of Project-Based Learning in Developing Digital Literacy Among Undergraduates. *Charoula M. Angeli, University of Cyprus; Ourania Miliou, University of Cyprus*

It's Not About the Money: Obstacles and Challenges With Scaling Up Problem-based Learning (PBL) School Transformation. *Paul S Sutton, Pacific Lutheran University*

Chair: *Vanessa Hammler Kenon, University of Texas - San Antonio*

94.042-7. Analytical Approaches, Tools, and Creations for Qualitative Inquiry (Table 7). SIG-Qualitative Research; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Writing to Know: Exploring Methodological Choices in a Narrative Inquiry. *Katharine Hull, University of South Florida*

Video as Partner: What Video Analysis Makes Visible in Ethnographic Classroom Research. *Megan K. Mitchell, University of Central Florida; Audra Skukauskaitė, University of Central Florida*

Verbal Protocol Analysis for Investigating Online Multimodal Reading. *Hyoju Ahn, Northern Illinois University; Hyeju Han, National Louis University*

Words that Wiggle to Wound: Critical race discourse analysis and preservice teachers' cultural autobiographies. *Kyle L. Chong, Michigan State University; Taneya Chavis, Michigan State University; Travon Jefferson, Michigan State University; Terry K. Flennaugh, Michigan State University; Terrance Burgess, Michigan State University; Maliyah H Drain, Michigan State University; Savannah Smith, John Jay College of Criminal Justice*

Chair: *Zulfukar Ozdogan, Indiana University*

Discussant: *Bismark Wiafe Bimpong, Ohio University*

94.042-8. Giftedness, Creativity, and Talent Roundtable: Behaviors and Learning Concepts (Table 8). SIG-

Research on Giftedness, Creativity and Talent; Roundtable Session

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Ground Floor, Gold 4; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

How Fifth Graders Solve Real-World Problems Using Science Knowledge. *Kamila Urban, Slovak Academy of Sciences; Ainur Kakimova, Institute for Research in Social Communication, SAS; Marek Urban, Czech Academy of Sciences*

Who is Discussed in Science of Reading Conversations? A Content Analysis. *Casey Hogan, University of Connecticut;*

Catherine A. Little, University of Connecticut
 Assessing the Empirical Support of Characteristics Lists of Gifted Students. *Matthew C. Makel, University of Calgary*
 Understanding Academic Motivation profiles Among Gifted Students in Fundamental Disciplines: A Q Methodology Study. *昱泽陈, Tsinghua University; peili yuan, 北京师范大学*
 STEM Identity and Career Intentions Among First-Year College Students: A Multi-Group Analysis. *Tugce Karatas, Purdue University; Nielsen Pereira, Purdue University/Gifted Education Research & Resource Institute*
 Chair: *Sarah A Caroleo, Brown University*

Division and SIG Posters

94.043. AERA Poster Session Sunday 1:45 pm; Poster Session

94.043-1. Academic Incongruities: Navigating Participatory Authorships within Hierarchical Knowledge. SIG-Grassroots Community and Youth Organizing for Educational Justice; Poster Session
 Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 1:45-3:15pm

Posters:

1. Academic Incongruities: Navigating Participatory Authorship within Hierarchical Knowledge Production Systems (Poster 1). *Bailey B. Smolarek, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Choua P. Xiong, University of Wisconsin - Oshkosh; Steven Yang, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Susan Vang, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Kayeng Yang, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Elijah Xiang Lin, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Kaj Tug Lee, University of Wisconsin - Madison*
2. Rooted: Exploring Youth of Color's Ancestral Archives (Poster 2). *Alexis E. Hunter, University of Colorado - Boulder*

94.043-2. A Collection of Studies Covering Varied Topics of Applied Research in Schools. Division H - Research, Evaluation and Assessment in Schools; Poster Session
 Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 1:45-3:15pm

Posters:

3. Both/And: Student Experiences of Culturally Responsive-Sustaining and Competency-Based Education in a Four-Year Initiative (Poster 3). *Jilliam N. Joe, Aurora Institute; Kelly Organ, FullScale*
4. Bright Spot Schools: Shining a Light on Strategies for Academic and Behavioral Success (Poster 4). *Colleen Graham Paeplow, Wake County Public School System; Anisa Clair Rhea, Wake County Public School System; Meghan Scrimgeour, Wake County Public School System;*

Ejike J. Edeh, University of Arkansas; Brittany Alligood, Wake County Public School System

5. Enhancing Student Engagement Through Instructional Fidelity: A Translational Research Partnership in an Urban Charter School (Poster 5). *Pallavi Aggarwal, University of Missouri - St. Louis; Natalie Bolton, University of Missouri - St. Louis*

94.043-3. Crisis Leadership and the Return to In-Person Schooling. Division A - Administration; Poster Session
 Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 1:45-3:15pm

Poster:

6. Evaluating School Climate Trends in Hawai'i – COVID-19 Pandemic and Return to In-Person Instruction (Poster 6). *Kiley Oeda, University of Hawaii - Manoa; Min Liu, Baylor University; Mark Murphy, University of Hawai'i at Manoa*

94.043-4. Motivation, Mindset, and Self-Regulated Learning. Division C - Learning and Instruction Cosponsored with SIG-Motivation in Education; Poster Session
 Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 1:45-3:15pm

Posters:

7. Academic support and college students' self-regulated learning: Can a summer course be effective? (Poster 7). *Minso Choi, The Ohio State University; Christopher A. Wolters, The Ohio State University*
8. Exploring Longitudinal Factor Structures of Situated Expectancy-Value Theory Constructs and Influence on Achievement (Poster 8). *Kyle C. Mefferd, HCA Healthcare; Chrisabelle Mefferd, Nevada State College; Jonathan C. Hilpert, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*
9. Gender Differences in Expectancy-Value Trajectories in Reading and Mathematics from Grades Four to Eight (Poster 9). *Yiwen Dong, Beijing Normal University; QIAN LI, Beijing Normal University*
10. Motivated, but unchanged: How undergraduate research affects STEM students' expectancy-value beliefs and career intentions (Poster 10). *Trevor Tuma, University of Georgia; Erin L. Dolan, University of Georgia*
11. Motivation to Teach and Self-Efficacy in Multicultural STEM Classrooms: A Correlational Study (Poster 11). *Romario Montaña-Ramos, Texas Tech University; Ngoc Kim Tuyen Pham, Texas Tech University; Xuan He, Texas Tech University*
12. Parenting Styles and Children's Academic Achievement: The Mediating role of Growth Mindset and Academic Self-efficacy (Poster 12). *Ruobing Wang, East China Normal University*
13. PhD Students' Research Motivational Profiles and Their Relations with Research Agendas (Poster 13). *Fei Cao, Nanjing Normal University; Siyao Chen, University of Hong Kong; Mengting LI, Nanjing Normal University; Weiqiao*

Fan, Shanghai Normal University; Li-Fang Zhang, University of Hong Kong

14. The Validation of the Student Homework Goal Orientation Scale (Poster 14). *Jianzhong Xu, Mississippi State University; Ruiping Yuan, Mississippi State University; Chuang Wang, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Daina Zhu, Mississippi State University*
15. The Validation of the Student Homework Mindset Scale (Poster 15). *Jianzhong Xu, Mississippi State University; Ruiping Yuan, Mississippi State University; Chuang Wang, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Daina Zhu, Mississippi State University; Ha Thi Viet Nguyen, Ton Duc Thang University*
16. University Students' Engagement in AI-Assisted Learning: A Situated Expectancy-Value Theory (SEVT) Perspective (Poster 16). *TING TIAN, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Jiajing LI, Beijing Normal University; Vivian WY LEE, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Ronnel B. King, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Ching Sing Chai, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Ziqi Mao, The Chinese University of Hong Kong*
17. The role of emotion regulation self-efficacy in regulating achievement emotions (Poster 17). *LUYAO XU, McGill University; Shi Yu, Purdue University; Cuilin Li, The University of Hong Kong; Junzhu Su, McGill University; Shasha Li, McGill University; Nikki G. Lobczowski, McGill University*
18. A Situated Expectancy-Value Perspective for Understanding ADHD in College Students (Poster 18). *Victoria A Boldt, Reed College; Jennifer Henderlong Corpus, Reed College*
19. Beyond the Leaky Pipeline: Purpose-Driven Career Transitions from Traditional Science Pathways to Meaningful Work (Poster 19). *Garam A. Lee, Michigan State University; Goun Choi, Michigan State University; Tony Perez, Old Dominion University; Lisa Linnenbrink-Garcia, Michigan State University*

94.043-5. Student Engagement and Approaches to Teaching in Engineering. Division C - Learning and Instruction; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 1:45-3:15pm

Posters:

20. Longitudinal Role of Engagement in Academic Performance among Vocational High School Students in Engineering Programs (Poster 20). *Yu-Heng Chen, National Taiwan Normal University; Hsun-Yu Chan, National Taiwan Normal University*
21. Exploring Interactions during Primary Grades Small Group Engineering (Poster 21). *Daria Poliakova, University of North Florida; Meghan M. Parkinson, University of North Florida; Raven Robinson-Wilson, University of North Florida; Syeda Hyder, Florida State College - Jacksonville*

22. Exploring Divergent Student Perceptions of Importance and Enjoyment in Engineering Summer Camp Activities: Implications for Inclusive and Interest-Driven Program Design (Poster 22). *Jae Hoon Lim, University of North Carolina - Charlotte; Sohee Kim, University of South Alabama*
23. Capturing EM-Focused Instruction: Development and Validation of a Teaching Practices Inventory for Undergraduate Engineering Faculty (Poster 23). *Shukufe Rahman, The Ohio State University; Md Ulfat Tahsin, The Ohio State University; Bryant Hutson, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Marcus Vinicius Melo de Lyra, The Ohio State University; Benjamin Ahn, The Ohio State University*
24. The Impact of an Interdisciplinary Biology-Engineering Summer Program on High School Students' Self-Efficacy and Interest (Poster 24). *Anna Fricano DeJarnette, University of Cincinnati; Anushri Shankar, University of Cincinnati; Stephanie Rollmann, University of Cincinnati; John E. Layne, University of Cincinnati; Dieter Vanderelst, University of Cincinnati*

94.043-6. Platforms of Practice: Teacher Identity in Digital Spaces. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 1:45-3:15pm

Posters:

25. A Qualitative Exploration of Online Discussion Facilitation and Pre-service Teacher Identity Development (Poster 25). *Hürriyet Sarıdemir, Middle East Technical University; Nur Cakir, Middle East Technical University*
26. Care, Community, and Digital Technologies: Areas of Integration and Tension in Pandemic-Prepared Teachers' Identity Systems (Poster 26). *Amy Guillotte, University of Pennsylvania*
27. Constructing "Good Teaching" Online: Teacher Influencers and the Politics of Professional Identity (Poster 27). *Anne E. Martin, Georgia State University*
28. Exploring CFL Teacher Identity through Podcasts: Positioning, Agency, and Social Justice in Cross-Cultural Contexts (Poster 28). *Jingning He, University at Buffalo - SUNY; Zhehan Zheng, University at Buffalo - SUNY*

94.043-7. Innovative Design and Models for Teaching and Teacher Education - Div K Section 09. Division K - Teaching and Teacher Education; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 1:45-3:15pm

Posters:

29. Empowering Teachers as Creators of Pedagogical Agents: An Integrated Perspective of Constructionism, ICAP, and TPACK (Poster 29). *Shuang Li, University of Hong Kong; Haiyang Xin, COCOROBO Limited; Yahui Yu, COCOROBO*

Limited; *Lei Gao, The Chinese University of Hong Kong; Qiannan Niu, COCOROBO Limited; Ching Sing Chai, Chinese University of Hong Kong; Lingyun Huang, The Education University of Hong Kong*

30. Reclaiming Legitimacy in Teacher Preparation: Using Core Teaching Practices to Structure Clinical Experience (Poster 30). *Cynthia L. Carver, Oakland University; Audra Slocum, Oakland University; Anthony Tuf Francis, Oakland University*
31. Teaching with Technology: Using Rehearsal and Video Analysis for Reflective Practice (Poster 31). *WenYen Huang, SUNY - College at New Paltz*
32. Visibility of Teaching in Mathematics Teachers' Professional Development (Poster 32). *Ruya Savuran, University of Michigan; Patricio G. Herbst, University of Michigan; Amanda Marie Milewski, University of Michigan; Soobin Jeon, University of Michigan*

94.043-8. Methodological Techniques for Challenging Data and Modeling Situations. SIG-Educational Statisticians; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 1:45-3:15pm

Posters:

33. Beyond Diagnostics: Tools for Consideration of Least-Squares Influential Data (Poster 33). *John D. Morris, Florida Atlantic University; Mary G. Lieberman, Florida Atlantic University; Maria D. Vásquez-Colina, Florida Atlantic University*
34. Bridging Theory, Data, and Method: A Framework for Modeling Heterogeneous Treatment Effects in Educational Research (Poster 34). *Jee-Seon Kim, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Graham Ward Buhrman, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Xiangyi Liao, University of British Columbia*
35. Factors Affecting Teachers' Intention to Leave: An Exploratory Study using Machine Learning and Logistic Regression (Poster 35). *Tzu-Wei Wang, Virginia Commonwealth University; Michael Broda, Virginia Commonwealth University; Georgia Heyward, Virginia Commonwealth University; Cammie Justus-Smith, Virginia Commonwealth University*

94.043-9. Experiential Education and Community Engagement: Scholarship and Practice SIG Poster Session. SIG-Experiential Education and Community Engagement: Scholarship and Practice; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 1:45-3:15pm

Posters:

36. Expanding Global Understanding through Local Community-Engaged Learning (Poster 36). *Julia Bach, Wheaton College; Alia Bicbic, University of Minnesota; Julia Goettl, University of Minnesota; Julia Grote, University of Minnesota; Laurel Hirt, University of*

Minnesota; Megan Reed, University of Minnesota

37. Experiential and critical service-learning: Course components that matter (Poster 37). *Elizabeth Gayle Soslau, University of Delaware*
38. Experiential interdisciplinary STEAM learning: Students' perceptions of their social and environmental responsibilities as citizens (Poster 38). *Kevin O'Connor, Mount Royal University*
39. From Informal Learning to Community-Engaged Engineering: A Framework for Community Participation in Engineering for Social Good (Poster 39). *Chih Hsuan Lin, University of Florida; Andrea Ramirez-Salgado, University of Florida; Pasha Antonenko, University of Florida*
40. SEMBRAR: Sustainable, Environmental, Multidisciplinary, Bilingual Research and Advocacy in Rurality (Poster 40). *Lourdes Cardozo-Gaibisso, Mississippi State University; Leynar Leyton Naranjo, University of Florida*
41. The Haven Center: An Exploration of Alumni's Civic Engagement, Identity, and Self-Esteem (Poster 41). *Jessica Cetin, Teach For America, Inc.; Izabela Taylor, Amgen; Quinterrence Bell, Vista College Prep*
42. The Reflective Compass: Transforming Global Learning Experiences into Future Innovative Practice (Poster 42). *Theresa Dawson, Pepperdine University*
43. Ceding Space, Seeding Emancipation with Alternative School Students (Poster 43). *Sean Forbes, Auburn University; Carey E. Andrzejewski, Auburn University; Eric Hogan, Georgia Southern University*
44. Unforgetting Communities: Preparing Future Educators through a Community-Based Education Course (Poster 44). *Quaylan Allen, Chapman University; Cristie Suzukawa Clancy, Chapman University; Kylie Cosette Parks, Chapman University; Mercedes Washington, Chapman University; Maya Yesharim, University of Denver*

94.043-10. Systemic, Critical, and Applied Perspectives on Technology Integration. SIG-Technology as an Agent of Change in Teaching and Learning; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 1:45-3:15pm

Posters:

45. Whose Voices Lead? Analyzing Gendered Authorship Trends in Educational Technology Journals from 2019 to 2024 (Poster 45). *Loraine Cisternas-Garcia, University of Florida; Nazanin Adhami, University of Florida; Lauren Weisberg, University of Texas - Arlington; Christine Wusylko, Kennesaw State University; Elfa Nur Iftitah, University of Florida; Yi-Pin Wei, University of Florida; Kara M. Dawson, University of Florida*
46. Truth and Presence: Leveraging Smartphones and AI for Participatory Action Research (Poster 46). *S. Otto Khera, New Mexico State University*
47. Institutional Predictors of Technology Integration in U.S. Schools: Laying the Groundwork for AI with FRSS 110

Data (Poster 47). *Bridget Newell, University of Florida; Nazanin Adhami, University of Florida*

48. SARA: AI-Assisted Self-Applied Tool for Reading Screening in Dominican Schools (Poster 48). *Daniel Cubilla-Bonnetier, Universidad Iberoamericana; Enzo Casamassima, Universidad Iberoamericana; Laura Virginia Sánchez-Vincitore, Universidad Iberoamericana*

94.043-11. Research on teaching and learning in educational psychology: Posters. SIG-Teaching Educational Psychology; Poster Session
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level Two, Poster Hall - Exhibit Hall A; 1:45-3:15pm

Posters:

49. Educational psychology: What should be taught, when, and to whom? (Poster 49). *Elizabeth A. Kraatz, Purdue University; Anna C. Brady, Georgia Southern University*
50. Growth Trajectories of Self-Rated Health and Life Satisfaction Across Student Transition in China (Poster 50). *Yuxin Guo, Dalian University of Technology; Xinqiao Liu, Tianjin University*
51. The Invisible Pillar: Challenges Facing Educational Psychology and its Place in Teacher Preparation (Poster 51). *Anna C. Brady, Georgia Southern University; Elizabeth A. Kraatz, Purdue University*
52. Zines as Summative Assessment for Learning: Reimagining Rigor Through Creativity and Learning as Becoming (Poster 52). *April Ursula Fox, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Nicole J. Thomas, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*

94.044. e-Lightning Ed-Talk Session 23 - Stage 1. AERA e-Lightning Ed-Talks; AERA Ed Talk
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Exhibit Hall A - Stage 1; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

- Capturing EM-Focused Instruction: Development and Validation of a Teaching Practices Inventory for Undergraduate Engineering Faculty (Stage 1, 1:50 PM). *Shukufe Rahman, The Ohio State University; Md Ulfat Tahsin, The Ohio State University; Bryant Hutson, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill; Marcus Vinicius Melo de Lyra, The Ohio State University; Benjamin Ahn, The Ohio State University*
- Parenting Styles and Children's Academic Achievement: The Mediating role of Growth Mindset and Academic Self-efficacy (Stage 1, 2:08 PM). *Ruobing Wang, East China Normal University*
- Beyond the Leaky Pipeline: Purpose-Driven Career Transitions from Traditional Science Pathways to Meaningful Work (Stage 1, 2:17 PM). *Garam A. Lee, Michigan State University; Goun Choi, Michigan State University; Tony Perez, Old Dominion University; Lisa Linnenbrink-Garcia, Michigan State University*

Bright Spot Schools: Shining a Light on Strategies for

Academic and Behavioral Success (Stage 1, 2:26 PM). *Colleen Graham Paepflow, Wake County Public School System; Anisa Clair Rhea, Wake County Public School System; Meghan Scrimgeour, Wake County Public School System; Ejike J. Edeh, University of Arkansas; Brittany Alligood, Wake County Public School System*

Constructing "Good Teaching" Online: Teacher Influencers and the Politics of Professional Identity (Stage 1, 2:35 PM). *Anne E. Martin, Georgia State University*

Reclaiming Legitimacy in Teacher Preparation: Using Core Teaching Practices to Structure Clinical Experience (Stage 1, 2:44 PM). *Cynthia L. Carver, Oakland University; Audra Slocum, Oakland University; Anthony Tuf Francis, Oakland University*

Chair: *Erika A. Patall, University of Southern California*

94.045. e-Lightning Ed-Talk Session 23 - Stage 2. AERA e-Lightning Ed-Talks; AERA Ed Talk
Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Exhibit Hall A - Stage 2; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

- Beyond Diagnostics: Tools for Consideration of Least-Squares Influential Data (Stage 2, 1:50 PM). *John D. Morris, Florida Atlantic University; Mary G. Lieberman, Florida Atlantic University; Maria D. Vásquez-Colina, Florida Atlantic University*
- Factors Affecting Teachers' Intention to Leave: An Exploratory Study using Machine Learning and Logistic Regression (Stage 2, 1:59 PM). *Tzu-Wei Wang, Virginia Commonwealth University; Michael Broda, Virginia Commonwealth University; Georgia Heyward, Virginia Commonwealth University; Cammie Justus-Smith, Virginia Commonwealth University*
- Expanding Global Understanding through Local Community-Engaged Learning (Stage 2, 2:08 PM). *Julia Bach, Wheaton College; Alia Bicbic, University of Minnesota; Julia Goettl, University of Minnesota; Julia Grote, University of Minnesota; Laurel Hirt, University of Minnesota; Megan Reed, University of Minnesota*
- Experiential interdisciplinary STEAM learning: Students' perceptions of their social and environmental responsibilities as citizens (Stage 2, 2:17 PM). *Kevin O'Connor, Mount Royal University*
- The Haven Center: An Exploration of Alumni's Civic Engagement, Identity, and Self-Esteem (Stage 2, 2:35 PM). *Jessica Cetin, Teach For America, Inc.; Izabela Taylor, Amgen; Quinterrence Bell, Vista College Prep*
- The Reflective Compass: Transforming Global Learning Experiences into Future Innovative Practice (Stage 2, 2:44 PM). *Theresa Dawson, Pepperdine University*

Chair: *Michael P. Cohen, American Institutes for Research*

94.046. e-Lightning Ed-Talk Session 23 - Stage 3. AERA e-Lightning Ed-Talks; AERA Ed Talk

Los Angeles Convention Center, Level One, Exhibit Hall A
- Stage 3; 1:45-3:15pm

Participants:

Rooted: Exploring Youth of Color's Ancestral Archives (Stage 3, 1:50 PM). *Alexis E. Hunter, University of Colorado - Boulder*

Academic Incongruities: Navigating Participatory Authorship within Hierarchical Knowledge Production Systems (Stage 3, 1:59 PM). *Bailey B. Smolarek, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Choua P. Xiong, University of Wisconsin - Oshkosh; Steven Yang, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Susan Vang, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Kayeng Yang, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Elijah Xiang Lin, University of Wisconsin - Madison; Kaj Tug Lee, University of Wisconsin - Madison*

Zines as Summative Assessment for Learning: Reimagining Rigor Through Creativity and Learning as Becoming (Stage 3, 2:08 PM). *April Ursula Fox, University of Nevada - Las Vegas; Nicole J. Thomas, University of Nevada - Las Vegas*

Whose Voices Lead? Analyzing Gendered Authorship Trends in Educational Technology Journals from 2019 to 2024 (Stage 3, 2:17 PM). *Loraine Cisternas-Garcia, University of Florida; Nazanin Adhami, University of Florida; Lauren Weisberg, University of Texas - Arlington; Christine Wusylko, Kennesaw State University; Elfa Nur Ifitah, University of Florida; Yi-Pin Wei, University of Florida; Kara M. Dawson, University of Florida*

Truth and Presence: Leveraging Smartphones and AI for Participatory Action Research (Stage 3, 2:26 PM). *S. Otto Khera, New Mexico State University*

Chairs: *Bianca Jontae Baldrige, Harvard University; P. Karen Murphy, Pennsylvania State University*

JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, Platinum G & H;
8:00am to 4:00pm

Chair: *Liesel Ebersohn, University of Pretoria*

Participants: *Bee Leng Chua, National Institute of Education - Nanyang Technological University; Joe O'Hara, Dublin City University; Geovana Mendonça Lunardi Mendes, Universidade do Estado de Santa Catarina; Rocío García-Carrion, University of Deusto; Mustafa Yunus Eryaman, Canakkale Onsekiz Mart University; Tabbye M. Chavous, American Educational Research Association; Carine Jonker, World Education Research Association; Gunjana Kuntamarat, World Education Research Association*

Monday, April 13th, 7:00 am

WERA Sessions

95.010. World Education Research Association Council Breakfast, Lunch and Breakout Room (Closed). World Education Research Association; Reception
JW Marriott Los Angeles L.A. LIVE, 2nd Floor, Platinum I;
7:00am to 4:00pm

Monday, April 13th, 8:00 am

WERA Sessions

96.010. World Education Research Association Council Meeting (Closed). World Education Research Association;
Board Meeting